

Pandigital Equivalent Selfie Fractions¹

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Abstract

The **addable fractions** are proper fraction where addition can be inserted into numerator and denominator, and the resulting fraction is equal to the original. The same is true for other operations, such as, **addition, multiplication, potentiation**, etc. For more details refer author's work [10]. This work bring **mixed selfie fractions** with all operations using 10 digits, known by **pandigital selfie fractions**. This work brings maximum up to 91 equivalent fractions. The fractions are without repetition of digits

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¹This paper revises and extend considerably author's previous two works <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a116.pdf> [8] and <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a117.pdf> [9] done in 2016.

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1 Introduction

Kieth [2, 3] for the first gave an idea of **dottable fraction**. It is a proper fraction where multiplication signs can be inserted into numerator and denominator, and the resulting fraction is equal to the original. Keith's [2, 3] idea was only with multiplication. For the first time, we extended it to other operations also, such as, with **addition, multiplication, potentiation**, etc. separately or jointly. We can think all of them together also. See below some examples studied by author [5, 6, 7, 8, 9].

1.1 Selfie Fraction

- **Addable Fractions**

$$\frac{96}{352} = \frac{9+6}{3+52}, \frac{182}{6734} = \frac{18+2}{6+734}, \text{ etc.} \quad (1)$$

- **Subtractable Fractions**

$$\frac{204}{357} = \frac{20-4}{35-7}, \frac{726}{1089} = \frac{72-6}{108-9}, \text{ etc.} \quad (2)$$

- **Dottable Fraction**

$$\frac{13}{624} = \frac{1 \times 3}{6 \times 24}, \frac{416}{728} = \frac{4 \times 16}{7 \times 2 \times 8}, \text{ etc.} \quad (3)$$

- **Dottable with Potentiation Fractions**

$$\frac{95}{342} = \frac{9 \times 5}{3^4 \times 2}, \frac{728}{1456} = \frac{7^2 \times 8}{14 \times 56}, \text{ etc.} \quad (4)$$

- **Mixed Fractions: All Operations**

$$\frac{4980}{5312} = \frac{4-9+80}{5 \times (3+1)^2}, \frac{3249}{5168} = \frac{(3+2^4) \times 9}{(5-1) \times 68}, \text{ etc.} \quad (5)$$

Observing the examples given in (1) - (5), the numerator and denominator follows the same order of digits in both sides of each fraction separated by operations. These type of fractions, we call **Selfie fractions**. There are two situations. One when all digits appearing in each fraction are distinct and second, when there are repetitions of digits. Initially, we shall work with distinct digits. Due to big number of fractions, the repetition of digits shall be dealt elsewhere. The idea of **equivalent e fractions** is explained below.

1.2 Equivalent Selfie Fractions

Above we have given *selfie fractions* with single value in each case. There are many fractions, that can be written in more than one way, for example,

- **Equivalent: Addable**

$$\frac{1453}{2906} = \frac{1+453}{2+906} = \frac{145+3}{290+6} = \frac{1+45+3}{2+90+6}, \text{ etc.} \quad (6)$$

- **Equivalent: Subtractable**

$$\frac{932}{1864} = \frac{9-32}{18-64} = \frac{93-2}{186-4}, \text{ etc.} \quad (7)$$

- **Equivalent: Dottable and Addable**

$$\frac{1680}{59472} = \frac{1 \times 6 \times 80}{59 \times 4 \times 72} = \frac{1+6+8+0}{59+472}, \text{ etc.} \quad (8)$$

- **Equivalent: Dottable, Addable and Subtractable**

$$\frac{302}{8154} = \frac{30 \times 2}{81 \times 5 \times 4} = \frac{3+02}{81+54} = \frac{3-02}{81-54}, \text{ etc.} \quad (9)$$

- **Symmetric Equivalent: Addable and Subtractable**

$$\frac{645}{1290} = \frac{6-45}{12-90} = \frac{6+45}{12+90}, \text{ etc.} \quad (10)$$

- **Equivalent: Dottable and Addable together**

$$\frac{284}{639} = \frac{2 \times 8 + 4}{6 + 39} = \frac{28 + 4}{6 \times (3 + 9)}, \text{ etc.} \quad (11)$$

- **Equivalent: Mixed - All Operations**

$$\frac{73842}{90516} = \frac{7-3 \times (8-4^2)}{9 \times 05-1-6} = \frac{7 \times (3+8) + 4^2}{90 + (5-1) \times 6} = \frac{738+4+2}{905+1+6}, \text{ etc.} \quad (12)$$

Equivalent expressions given in (8), let us classify them as **symmetric equivalent fractions**. In this case we just change plus with minus and vice-versa. There are many **double symmetric equivalent fraction** too. The previous work done by author in 2016 is distributed as follows:

- (i) Selfie Fractions: Addable - [5];
- (ii) Selfie Fractions: Dottable and Pontentiable - [6];
- (iii) Selfie Fractions: Addable and Dottable Together - [7];
- (iv) Equivalent Selfie Fractions: Dottable, Addable and Subtractable - [8];
- (v) Equivalent Selfie Fractions: Addable and Dottable Together - [9].

The combined and enlarged version of above five items can seen in author's recent work [10]. In this work our aim is to bring **pandigital selfie fractions** with all basic operations having 10-digits non repeated in each fraction. These fractions are with single and multiple representations. The maximum there are 91 equivalent representations of same fraction. Some special type pandigital selfie fractions can also be seen in [10]. For equivalent fractions see authors another works [11, 12]. For authors work on numbers in different situations refer [13, 14].

Remark 1.1. *The following two situations are considered:*

(i) *The first number of the r.h.s of the fraction are always positive, for example,*

$$\frac{21564}{97038} := \frac{4 + 1508}{7 + 2639}.$$

The following expression also give selfie fraction,

$$\frac{21564}{97038} := \frac{-4 + 1508}{-7 + 2639}.$$

This kind of expressions are not considered as the first members of numerator and denominator are negative.

(ii) *Even though, the final expression is positive, but the numerator and denominator are not considered negative, for example,*

$$\frac{21564}{97038} := \frac{2 + 1564}{9 + 7038} := \frac{2 - 1564}{9 - 7038}$$

*The aim of excluding these two items is because allowing them there is chance of unnecessary **equivalent selfie fraction** repetitions.*

*The **selfie fractions** are considered in such a way that first number on the left side is always positive, and the difference among the terms of numerators and denominators are also positive. Also the fraction are with **non repeated 10 digits, i.e, 0 to 9.***

2 Pandigital Single Representations Selfie Fractions

2.1 Five Digit's Numerator

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10286}{39754} := \frac{10 + 286}{(3 \times 97 - 5) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10368}{74592} := \frac{1 \times 0 + 36 \times 8}{74 \times (5 + 9) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{72468} := \frac{1 + 039 - 5}{7 \times (2 + 4) \times 6 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10293}{47658} := \frac{10^2 - 9 \times 3}{(4 + 7) \times 6 \times 5 + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10368}{74952} := \frac{(10 - 3) \times 6 \times 8}{7^4 + (9 + 5) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{76824} := \frac{(10 \times 3 - 9) \times 5}{768 + 2 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10293}{64578} := \frac{10^2 - 9 \times 3}{6 - 4 + 57 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10368}{97524} := \frac{(1 - 03 + 6) \times 8}{9 + (75 - 2) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{78246} := \frac{(10 + 3 + 9) \times 5}{782 + 46}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10296}{83754} := \frac{10 - 2 + 96}{837 + 5 + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10374}{92568} := \frac{1 - 03 + 7 \times 4}{((9 - 2) \times 5 - 6) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{82764} := \frac{(10 \times 3 - 9) \times 5}{8^2 \times (7 + 6) + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10325}{97468} := \frac{10 \times 3 \times 2 \times 5}{(9 \times 7 - 4) \times 6 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{46728} := \frac{(10 \times 3 - 9) \times 5}{4 \times (6 + 7 \times 2 \times 8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{86427} := \frac{(10 \times 3 - 9) \times 5}{864 + 2 + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10354}{97862} := \frac{1 \times 035 - 4}{97 + (8 + 6)^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{46827} := \frac{(10 \times 3 - 9) \times 5}{468 - 2 + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10396}{27485} := \frac{10^3 - 96}{2 + 7^4 - 8 - 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10368}{29754} := \frac{(1 + 03) \times 6 \times 8}{2 + 9 \times (7 + 54)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{46872} := \frac{(10 + 3 + 9) \times 5}{4 \times (6 + 8 \times 7) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10437}{59682} := \frac{1 \times 0 + 4^3 + 7}{(5 \times 9 + 6) \times 8 - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10368}{52974} := \frac{(1 + 03) \times 6 \times 8}{5 + 2 + 974}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{47628} := \frac{(10 + 3 + 9) \times 5}{476 + 28}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{10439}{75628} := \frac{104 + 39}{(7 + 5 \times 6) \times 28}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{10452}{76983} := \frac{1^{04} \times 52}{7 \times 6 \times 9 + 8 - 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10692}{47385} := \frac{(10 - 6) \times (9 + 2)}{(4 - 7 \times (3 - 8)) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10836}{45927} := \frac{10 + 8^3 - 6}{(4 + 5) \times 9 \times 27}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10465}{73892} := \frac{104 + 6 + 5}{7 \times (3 \times 8 + 92)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10692}{53784} := \frac{1 \times 0 + 6 \times (9 + 2)}{(5 + 37) \times 8 - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10854}{62937} := \frac{10 \times (8 + 5) + 4}{(6 \times 2 \times 9 + 3) \times 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10465}{97382} := \frac{10 \times 46 - 5}{9 + (73 - 8)^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10692}{57348} := \frac{(1 + 06) \times (9 + 2)}{5 \times 73 + 48}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10854}{73629} := \frac{108 \times 5 - 4}{7 + 3629}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10476}{92538} := \frac{(1 - 04 + 7) \times 6}{92 + 5 \times 3 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10695}{34782} := \frac{1 \times 069 \times 5}{3 \times (47 \times 8 - 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10857}{63294} := \frac{1 \times 0 + 8 \times 5 + 7}{6 \times (3 + 2) \times 9 + 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10549}{26873} := \frac{105 \times 4 - 9}{2 \times 6 \times 87 + 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10695}{74382} := \frac{10 \times (6 + 9) + 5}{7 \times (4 \times 38 + 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10863}{49572} := \frac{1 \times 0 + 8 + 63}{4 \times (95 - 7 \times 2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10564}{79382} := \frac{10 \times 56 - 4}{(7 + 9)^3 + 82}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10735}{26894} := \frac{10 \times (7 + 3) - 5}{2 + (68 - 9) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10863}{49725} := \frac{1 \times 0 + 8 + 63}{(4 + 9 \times 7 - 2) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10569}{28743} := \frac{1 + 05 \times 6 \times 9}{2 - 8 + 743}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10735}{49268} := \frac{10 \times (7 + 3) - 5}{4 \times 92 + 68}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10863}{94572} := \frac{1 \times 0 + 8 + 6 + 3}{(9 \times (4 + 5) - 7) \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10584}{29736} := \frac{1 + 05 \times (8 - 4)}{(2 + 9) \times 7 - 3 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10738}{46592} := \frac{(10 + 7) \times 3 + 8}{4^{6+5-9+2}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10935}{24867} := \frac{1 \times 0 + 9 \times 3 \times 5}{(2 + 48) \times 6 + 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10584}{62937} := \frac{(10 \times 5 - 8) \times 4}{62 + 937}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10738}{69524} := \frac{(10 + 7) \times 3 + 8}{6 \times 9 \times (5 + 2) + 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10935}{26487} := \frac{1 + 09 + 35}{26 - 4 + 87}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10634}{29857} := \frac{10 + 6 \times (3 + 4)}{2 - 9 \times 8 \times (5 - 7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10745}{69382} := \frac{(10 - 7 + 4) \times 5}{6 \times 9 \times 3 + 8^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10935}{47628} := \frac{1 + 09 + 35}{4 \times 7 \times 6 + 28}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10642}{59783} := \frac{10^{6-4} + 2}{597 - 8 \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10764}{23598} := \frac{(1 \times 07 + 6) \times 4}{2 \times (3 + 5) + 98}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10935}{48672} := \frac{10 \times (9 + 3)^5}{4^8 \times (6 + 7)^2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10647}{53928} := \frac{1 + 06 \times 4 \times 7}{(5^3 - 9 \times 2) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10764}{25389} := \frac{10 \times (7 \times 6 + 4)}{2 \times 538 + 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10935}{84672} := \frac{1 \times 0 + 9^3 \times 5}{((8 - 4) \times (6 \times 7))^2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10647}{59283} := \frac{1 + 06 \times 4 \times 7}{59 \times 2 \times 8 - 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10764}{28359} := \frac{1 \times 0 + (7 + 6) \times 4}{2 \times 8 \times (3 + 5) + 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10947}{68352} := \frac{10 \times (9 + 4) - 7}{6 \times 8 \times (3 + 5) \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10647}{85293} := \frac{(1 + 064) \times 7}{(8 - 5 + 2) \times 9^3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10764}{38259} := \frac{(10 + 7 + 6) \times 4}{3 \times (8^2 + 5 \times 9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10962}{38745} := \frac{(1 + 09) \times 6 - 2}{(3 \times (8 + 7) - 4) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10653}{29748} := \frac{106 \times (5 - 3)}{2 \times (9 + 7 \times 4) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10764}{38295} := \frac{1 \times 0 + (7 + 6) \times 4}{3 - 8 + 2 \times 95}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10962}{43587} := \frac{(10 \times 9 - 6) \times 2}{4 \times (3 \times 58 - 7)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10653}{97284} := \frac{1^{06} \times 53}{(9 + 7 \times 2 \times 8) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10783}{62594} := \frac{1 + 078 + 3}{(6 + 2) \times 59 + 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10962}{45738} := \frac{(10 + 9) \times 6 + 2}{4 + (57 + 3) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10658}{39274} := \frac{10 \times 6 \times 5 - 8}{(3 \times 92 - 7) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10792}{38456} := \frac{10 + 7 \times 9 - 2}{3 \times 84 - 5 + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10962}{48573} := \frac{(1 + 09) \times 6 - 2}{4 \times (8 + 57) - 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10659}{38247} := \frac{1 \times 06 + 5 \times 9}{3 \times (8^2 + 4 - 7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10829}{64753} := \frac{(1 - 08) \times (2 - 9)}{6 \times 4 \times 7 + 5^3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10962}{57834} := \frac{(10 + 9) \times 6 + 2}{578 + 34}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10692}{35748} := \frac{1 + 06 + 92}{3^5 + (7 + 4) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10836}{42957} := \frac{-1 \times 08 + 36}{(4 + 2) \times 9 + 57}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10962}{85347} := \frac{1 + 09 + 6 - 2}{8 \times 5 \times 3 - 4 - 7}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{10963}{82574} := \frac{10+9 \times 63}{82 \times (57-4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12450}{68973} := \frac{1^{24} \times 50}{6-8 \times 9+7^3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12780}{64539} := \frac{1 \times 2^7 - 8 + 0}{645 - 39}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10965}{23478} := \frac{10+(9+6) \times 5}{2+3 \times 4 \times (7+8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12463}{89507} := \frac{1+2 \times (4 \times 6+3)}{8+9 \times (50-7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12789}{43065} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 78 - 9}{430 + 65}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10965}{27348} := \frac{10+(9 \times 65)}{2 \times (734+8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12480}{53976} := \frac{(1+2 \times 4) \times 80}{((5-3)^9+7) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12789}{45360} := \frac{1 \times 2^7 \times 8 - 9}{4 \times 5 \times 3 \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10965}{78432} := \frac{10+(9+6) \times 5}{(7+8+4) \times 32}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12483}{70956} := \frac{1+2 \times (4+8-3)}{7+095+6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12798}{36045} := \frac{1^2 \times 79 \times 8}{(360-4) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10974}{36285} := \frac{10 \times 9 - 7 \times 4}{3 \times (62+8) - 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12483}{70965} := \frac{1 \times 2 + 48 \times 3}{(70+96) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12798}{45360} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times (7+9 \times 8)}{4 \times 5^3 + 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12054}{63798} := \frac{1+2 \times 05 \times 4}{(6 \times 3+7) \times 9-8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12483}{76950} := \frac{1+2 \times (4+8) \times 3}{(7-6) \times (9 \times 50)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12798}{45603} := \frac{1^2 \times 79 \times 8}{4 \times (560+3)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12054}{93786} := \frac{1+2 \times 05 \times 4}{9 \times 37 - 8 - 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12483}{95760} := \frac{((1+2)^4 - 8) \times 3}{(9-5) \times (7 \times 60)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12798}{53460} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times (7+9 \times 8)}{(5 \times 3 - 4) \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12084}{35796} := \frac{1 \times (208+4)}{3+5^{7-9+6}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12495}{38760} := \frac{12 \times (4+9 \times 5)}{3 \times 8 \times 76) + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12834}{56079} := \frac{1 \times 2 + (8+3) \times 4}{5 \times (6 \times 07 - 9)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12087}{94563} := \frac{1 \times ((20 \times 8) - 7)}{(9 \times 45 - 6) \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12543}{69708} := \frac{125 - 4 \times 3}{6+9 \times 70 - 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12834}{75609} := \frac{1+2+8+3^4}{7-5+60 \times 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12096}{34587} := \frac{12^{09-6}}{3^4 \times (5+8 \times 7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12567}{38940} := \frac{1-2+5+67}{3 \times 8 \times 9+4+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12857}{49036} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times (8+5 \times 7)}{4+9 \times 036}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12096}{37548} := \frac{(1+20) \times 96}{(3+7) \times 5^4+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12573}{40986} := \frac{1 \times 257 - 3}{(40+98) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12864}{95073} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 8^{6-4}}{950 - 7 + 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12096}{38745} := \frac{1 \times 2^{0 \times 9+6}}{(3 \times (8+7) - 4) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12584}{37609} := \frac{12 \times (5 \times 8+4)}{3^7 - 609}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12870}{59436} := \frac{1-2+8 \times 7+0}{5-9+43 \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12096}{45738} := \frac{(1+2) \times 096}{4^5+73-8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12654}{83790} := \frac{1+(-2+6+5) \times 4}{8+3 \times 79+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12870}{64935} := \frac{128+70}{64+935}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12096}{48573} := \frac{1 \times 2^{0 \times 9+6}}{4 \times (8+57) - 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12670}{39458} := \frac{(1+2+6) \times 70}{394 \times 5 - 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12876}{39405} := \frac{(1 \times 2 + 8 \times 7) \times 6}{3 \times (9 \times 40 - 5)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12096}{57834} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 096}{(5 \times 7 - 8) \times 34}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12680}{95734} := \frac{(1-2+6) \times 8+0}{(95+7) \times 3-4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12876}{53940} := \frac{1+2-8+7 \times 6}{5 \times 39-40}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12096}{83475} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 096}{(8 \times 34 - 7) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12740}{86359} := \frac{1^2 \times 7 \times 40}{8+6 \times 35 \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12879}{36450} := \frac{12 \times 8+7 \times 9}{3^{6-4} \times 50}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12369}{45087} := \frac{(1+(2+3) \times 6) \times 9}{4^5+0 \times 8-7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12740}{89635} := \frac{1^2 \times 7 \times 4+0}{8+9 \times (6+3 \times 5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12879}{45360} := \frac{12 \times 8+7 \times 9}{4 \times 5^3+60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12369}{54870} := \frac{1-2 \times (3-69)}{5 \times (48+70)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12750}{38964} := \frac{(1+2 \times 7) \times 50}{3 \times (8 \times 96-4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12879}{53460} := \frac{12 \times 8+7 \times 9}{(5 \times 3-4) \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12397}{46508} := \frac{(1+(2+3) \times 9) \times 7}{4 \times 6 \times 50+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12768}{93450} := \frac{1^2 \times 76 \times 8}{(93-4) \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12935}{64078} := \frac{1 \times 2^9+3+5}{(6+40) \times 7 \times 8}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{12936}{78540} := \frac{12+9 \times 36}{(7 \times 8 - 5) \times 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13056}{29784} := \frac{1+30-5+6}{(2+9) \times 7-8+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13578}{40296} := \frac{1-3 \times (5-7-8)}{4 \times (029-6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12936}{85470} := \frac{1+2+9 \times (3+6)}{8+547+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13064}{59782} := \frac{1 \times 30 \times 6+4}{(59 \times 7+8) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13580}{94672} := \frac{1+3 \times 58+0}{94 \times (6+7)-2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12956}{38704} := \frac{1+2 \times (9+5 \times 6)}{3+8 \times 7 \times 04}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13064}{78952} := \frac{1+3 \times 06+4}{78+9+52}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13584}{60279} := \frac{1+3-(5-8) \times 4}{6-0+2+7 \times 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12958}{76043} := \frac{1^2+9 \times 5-8}{7+6^{0 \times 4+3}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13065}{29748} := \frac{(1+3) \times 065}{2 \times (9+7 \times 4) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{24597} := \frac{(1 \times 3+60) \times 8}{2 \times 459-7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12960}{37845} := \frac{(1+2) \times 96+0}{3-7+845}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13067}{59428} := \frac{1+30+6 \times 7}{5-9+42 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{24759} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 6 \times 08}{2 \times (4 \times 7 \times 5-9)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12960}{37854} := \frac{1^2 \times 960}{3^7-8+5^4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13072}{59684} := \frac{1+3+072}{5+9 \times (6+8 \times 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{25974} := \frac{(1 \times 3+60) \times 8}{2 \times (5 \times 97-4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12960}{48735} := \frac{1^2 \times 96+0}{4-8+73 \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13098}{52746} := \frac{13+098}{5-2+74 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{52974} := \frac{1 \times 36-08}{5 \times 2+9 \times (7+4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12960}{54378} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 960}{(5 \times 4)^3+7 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13248}{76590} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 24 \times 8}{(7+6 \times 5) \times 90}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{72954} := \frac{1 \times 36-0 \times 8}{7+2 \times 95-4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12960}{73584} := \frac{(1+2+9) \times 60}{7-3 \times 5+8^4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13250}{69748} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 250}{6 \times (9 \times 74-8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{74925} := \frac{(1 \times 3+60) \times 8}{(7-4) \times 925}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12960}{73845} := \frac{(1-2+9) \times 60}{7^3 \times 8-4-5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13254}{78960} := \frac{1+(3+2^5) \times 4}{7 \times 8 \times (9+6)+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{95742} := \frac{1+3+60-8}{(9+5) \times 7 \times 4+2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12960}{83745} := \frac{(1+2) \times 96+0}{837+4^5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13260}{98475} := \frac{1+3+2^6+0}{(9 \times (8+4)-7) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13624}{75980} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 62-4}{7 \times 5+980}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12960}{84375} := \frac{(1-2+9) \times 60}{((8-4) \times 3-7)^5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13284}{76950} := \frac{(1+32+8) \times 4}{(7-6) \times 950}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13629}{54870} := \frac{(13-6) \times (2+9)}{5 \times 48+70}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12963}{54087} := \frac{1+2 \times (9+63)}{5+(40 \times (8+7))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13480}{56279} := \frac{(1^3+4) \times 8+0}{5 \times 6+2^7+9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13629}{75048} := \frac{(13-6) \times (2+9)}{(7+50-4) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12987}{36504} := \frac{(1 \times 29+8) \times 7}{(3^6)-(5+(0-4))}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13509}{82476} := \frac{1-(3-5) \times 09}{8 \times 24-76}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13629}{78540} := \frac{1+362-9}{(7 \times 8-5) \times 40}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12987}{45630} := \frac{129+8 \times 7}{4 \times 5+630}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13524}{78960} := \frac{1+3^5 \times 2-4}{(7 \times 8-9) \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13650}{42987} := \frac{1^3 \times 650}{4 \times 2^9-8+7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13029}{67854} := \frac{1 \times 30^2+9}{6 \times (785+4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13528}{64970} := \frac{(135-2) \times 8}{(64+9) \times 70}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13680}{45927} := \frac{(1+3 \times 6) \times 80}{(4+5) \times 9^2 \times 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13048}{26795} := \frac{1 \times 30 \times 4-8}{2-6 \times (7-9 \times 5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13542}{69708} := \frac{(1+3 \times 5 \times 4) \times 2}{6+9 \times 70-8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13680}{59472} := \frac{(1+3 \times 6) \times 80}{(5+9) \times 472}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13054}{92876} := \frac{1+3 \times 05 \times 4}{(9-2) \times (8 \times 7+6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13542}{97680} := \frac{1+3 \times (5+4)^2}{(9+7+6) \times 80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13689}{25740} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times (6 \times 8-9)}{2^5 \times 7-4+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13056}{27948} := \frac{(1+3)^{05} \times 6}{2 \times (7+9^4+8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13572}{94068} := \frac{1+3+5 \times (7-2)}{9+4 \times 06 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13689}{74250} := \frac{13 \times (6 \times 8-9)}{(7+4) \times 250}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{13694}{20875} := \frac{1+3+6 \times (9+4)}{20 \times 8 - 7 \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13860}{45927} := \frac{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 60}{(4+5) \times 9 \times 27}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13968}{50472} := \frac{1 \times 396 - 8}{50 \times 4 \times 7 + 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13695}{80427} := \frac{(1^3 + 6 \times 9) \times 5}{804 \times 2 + 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13860}{59724} := \frac{1 \times 3 - 8 + 60}{5 + (9 + 7^2) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13968}{54720} := \frac{1 - (3 - 9 - 6) \times 8}{5 \times (4 + 72) + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13706}{29548} := \frac{13 + 70 - 6}{2 \times (95 - 4 - 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13860}{94752} := \frac{1 \times 3 - 8 + 60}{9 \times (47 - 5) - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13968}{74205} := \frac{(1 + 39) \times (6 + 8)}{7 \times (420 + 5)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13706}{45892} := \frac{13 + 70 + 6}{4 + 5 + (8 + 9)^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13860}{97524} := \frac{1 \times 3 - 8 + 60}{9 \times (7 \times 5 + 2 \times 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13986}{47250} := \frac{(13 + 98) \times 6}{(47 - 2) \times 50}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13708}{96254} := \frac{1 + 3 \times (7 + 08)}{9 + 62 \times 5 + 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13862}{54970} := \frac{1 - (3 - 8) \times 6 - 2}{54 - 9 + 70}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13986}{70245} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times (9 \times 8) + 6}{70 \times 2^4 - 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13720}{95648} := \frac{1 - 3 + 72 - 0}{(9 + 56 - 4) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13870}{92564} := \frac{1 + 3 \times 8 + 70}{9 + 25^{6-4}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13986}{72450} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times (9 \times 8) + 6}{(7 + 2^4) \times 50}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13725}{46890} := \frac{(1 + 3^{7-2}) \times 5}{4^6 + 8 \times 9 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13872}{95064} := \frac{1 + 3 + (8 + 7) \times 2}{9 + (50 + 6) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13986}{74025} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times (9 \times 8) + 6}{(7 + 40) \times 25}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13728}{56940} := \frac{(1 + 3) \times (7 \times 2 + 8)}{5 \times (69 + 4) + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13904}{28756} := \frac{1 + 39 - 0 + 4}{2 + 8 + 75 + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13987}{64025} := \frac{1 - 3 \times (9 - 8 \times 7)}{640 + 2 \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13746}{29058} := \frac{1 + 3 \times 7 \times 4 - 6}{2 \times 90 - 5 - 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13920}{75648} := \frac{1 + (3 + 9)^2 + 0}{756 + 4 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14025}{78693} := \frac{140 \times 2 - 5}{7 + (8 - 6)^9 \times 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13746}{29580} := \frac{1 + 3 \times 7 \times 4 - 6}{2 \times 9 \times 5 + 80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13920}{75864} := \frac{1 + 39 + 20}{7 + 5 \times 8^{6-4}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14025}{93687} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 025}{9^3 - 68 + 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13746}{82950} := \frac{(1 + 3)^{7-4} - 6}{(8 \times 2 - 9) \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13946}{58720} := \frac{1 + 3 - 9 + 4 \times 6}{(5 - 8 + 7) \times 20}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14035}{68972} := \frac{140 - 35}{6 \times (8 \times 9 + 7 \times 2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13795}{46280} := \frac{1 + 3 + 7 \times 9 - 5}{(4 \times 6 + 2) \times 8 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13960}{42578} := \frac{(1 + 39) \times 6 + 0}{4 \times (25 \times 7 + 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14039}{57268} := \frac{140 - 39}{5 \times 7 \times 2 \times 6 - 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13804}{67592} := \frac{1 + 3 \times 8 + 0 + 4}{(67 - 5 + 9) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13965}{20874} := \frac{13 \times (9 + 6) - 5}{2^{08} + 7 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14053}{96278} := \frac{1 + 40 + 53}{9 + 627 + 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13805}{94627} := \frac{1 \times (3 + 8) + 0 \times 5}{(9 + 4) \times (6^2 - 7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13965}{40278} := \frac{1 + 3 + 96 - 5}{(40 - 2) \times 7 + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14063}{25789} := \frac{1^4 + 06^3}{(2 + 5 \times 7) \times (8 + 9)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13824}{56970} := \frac{(1 - 3 + 8 - 2)^4}{5 + (6 + 9) \times 70}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13965}{47082} := \frac{(139 - 6) \times 5}{4 \times 70 \times 8 + 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14063}{78925} := \frac{1 \times 40 + 6 + 3}{(7 + 8) \times (9 \times 2) + 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13824}{57960} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 8 \times 24}{5 \times 7 \times (9 + 60)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13965}{87024} := \frac{1 + 3 + 96 - 5}{(8 + 70 \times 2) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14067}{29538} := \frac{1 + 40 \times (6 + 7)}{2 \times (9 + 538)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13824}{95760} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 8 \times 24}{95 \times 7 \times 6 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13968}{25704} := \frac{1 \times 396 - 8}{2 \times 5 + 704}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14067}{39528} := \frac{1 + 40 \times (6 + 7)}{3 \times (9 + 52) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13845}{60279} := \frac{1^3 \times 845}{60^2 + 79}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13968}{40752} := \frac{1 + (-3 + 9 + 6) \times 8}{40 \times 7 + 5 - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14067}{39852} := \frac{1 + 40 \times (6 + 7)}{3 \times (98 \times 5) + 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13860}{27594} := \frac{13 \times 8 + 6 - 0}{2 - 7 \times (5 - 9 \times 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13968}{45072} := \frac{1 + (-3 + 9 + 6) \times 8}{45 \times 07 - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14076}{25398} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 07 \times 6}{2^5 + 3 \times (9 + 8)}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{14076}{28359} := \frac{(1+40-7) \times 6}{28 \times 3 \times 5 - 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14350}{69782} := \frac{(1+4) \times 35 + 0}{69 + 782}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14685}{79032} := \frac{(1+4+6) \times 8 \times 5}{790 \times 3 - 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14076}{29835} := \frac{14 \times 07 - 6}{2 \times (98 - 3) + 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14382}{79560} := \frac{(1+4) \times 38 - 2}{(7+9) \times (5+60)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14697}{32085} := \frac{14 - 6 + 9 \times 7}{(3+20+8) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14076}{32589} := \frac{14 \times 07 - 6}{3 \times (2 \times 5 \times 8 - 9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14385}{70692} := \frac{(1 \times 4 + 3 \times 8) \times 5}{706 - 9 \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14706}{23598} := \frac{1^4 + 7 \times 06}{2 \times 35 - 9 + 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14076}{38295} := \frac{(1+40-7) \times 6}{3 \times (8+29) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14396}{57820} := \frac{(1+4)^3 - 9 + 6}{5 \times (78+20)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14706}{98325} := \frac{(1+4) \times 70 - 6}{(9+83) \times 25}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14076}{52938} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 07 \times 6}{5 - (2-9) \times (3 \times 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14508}{36972} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 50 + 8}{(3+69+7) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14725}{80693} := \frac{1 \times 4 - 7 \times (2-5)}{80 + 6 \times 9 + 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14076}{58293} := \frac{14 \times 07 - 6}{(5 \times 8 + 2) \times 9 + 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14508}{67392} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 50 + 8}{6 \times (7+39+2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14756}{20398} := \frac{1+4+7+56}{2 \times (039+8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14089}{76235} := \frac{1^4 + 08 \times 9}{76 \times 2 + 3^5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14508}{79236} := \frac{14 \times 5 + 08}{(79 - 2^3) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14760}{52398} := \frac{1^{47} \times 60}{5 \times (2+39) + 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14208}{75369} := \frac{(1 \times 4 - 2)^{08}}{7 \times (5^3 + 69)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14520}{73689} := \frac{1^4 \times 520}{7 \times (368+9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14760}{98523} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 76 + 0}{(9 + (8+5)^2) \times 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14250}{39786} := \frac{(1+4) \times 25 + 0}{397 - (8 \times 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14527}{80396} := \frac{1+4 \times (5^2 - 7)}{8 + 0396}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14805}{62937} := \frac{(1+48) \times 05}{62 + 937}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14256}{37098} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 2 \times (5+6)}{3 \times (70+9) - 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14560}{39872} := \frac{1^4 \times 5 + 60}{(3+9) \times (8+7) - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14805}{79632} := \frac{(1+48) \times 05}{79 \times (6 \times 3 - 2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14256}{38907} := \frac{1 + (4 - 2 + 5) \times 6}{3 + 8 \times (9 + 07)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14580}{73692} := \frac{1+4+5 \times 80}{7^3 \times 6 - 9 - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14805}{92637} := \frac{(1+48) \times 05}{(9+2^6) \times 3 \times 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14256}{70389} := \frac{1 - 4 + 25 - 6}{7 - 0 \times 3 + 8 \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14580}{97362} := \frac{1+4+5+80}{9 \times (73-6) - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14805}{92736} := \frac{(-1+48) \times 05}{92 \times (7+3+6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14256}{70983} := \frac{1+425+6}{(709+8) \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14592}{76038} := \frac{(1+4+59) \times 2}{7+60 \times (3+8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14820}{35796} := \frac{(1+4+8) \times 20}{3+5^{7-9+6}}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14256}{79380} := \frac{1+42-5+6}{7 \times (9 \times 3 + 8) + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14592}{76380} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times (5+9+2)}{7^{6-3} - 8 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14823}{76950} := \frac{(1-4+8^2) \times 3}{(7-6) \times 950}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14268}{73950} := \frac{(1+4) \times 2^6 + 8}{(7+3 \times 9) \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14596}{23780} := \frac{1-4+5 \times 9 \times 6}{(2+3) \times (7+80)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14823}{79605} := \frac{1+48+2+3}{(7-9+60) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14280}{35679} := \frac{(1+4^2) \times 80}{3+5 \times 679}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14625}{39078} := \frac{1+4 \times (6+25)}{390 - 7 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14823}{96075} := \frac{14+8^2+3}{(9+6) \times 07 \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14280}{36975} := \frac{14 \times 2 \times 8 + 0}{3+6 \times 97-5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14630}{92785} := \frac{1 \times 46 + 30}{92 + 78 \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14850}{76329} := \frac{1^{48} \times 50}{7 \times (6+32) - 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14280}{57936} := \frac{(1+4)^2 + 80}{5 \times 7 \times (9+3) + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14673}{80592} := \frac{1-4+673}{8 \times 05 \times 92}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14850}{76923} := \frac{(14-8) \times 50}{7 \times ((6+9)^2 - 3)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14280}{73695} := \frac{1^4 \times 280}{(7^3 - 6 \times 9) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14679}{35280} := \frac{1+4 \times (67-9)}{35 \times 2 \times 8 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14896}{23750} := \frac{(1+48) \times 96}{2 \times 3750}$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14928}{53760} := \frac{1+4+928}{(5+3) \times 7 \times 60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14976}{20358} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times (9-7)^6}{2 \times 03 \times 58}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14976}{35802} := \frac{1-4-9+76}{3-(5-80) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14976}{53280} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times (97-6)}{5 \times (3+2^8) + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14976}{53820} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times (9-7+6)}{5^3-8-2+0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14976}{58032} := \frac{1 \times 4-9+7+6}{5+8 \times 03+2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14976}{58320} := \frac{(1+4+9) \times 7+6}{5 \times (83-2) + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14985}{26307} := \frac{14-9+8 \times 5}{2 \times (6+30) + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14985}{32076} := \frac{((1+4) \times 9-8) \times 5}{320+76}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14985}{36720} := \frac{(1+4 \times 9) \times (8-5)}{36 \times 7+20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14985}{37260} := \frac{(1+4 \times 9) \times (8-5)}{3 \times 72+60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14985}{60273} := \frac{1+49+85}{60 \times (2+7) + 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14985}{67230} := \frac{1-49+85}{(6+7)^2-3+0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14985}{76302} := \frac{((1+4) \times 9-8) \times 5}{7 \times 6+30^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{14986}{73025} := \frac{(1+4) \times 9 \times 8-6}{(7^3+02) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15029}{84637} := \frac{1 \times 5 \times 02+9}{(8 \times 4+6) \times 3-7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15048}{29376} := \frac{1+50 \times 4+8}{2 \times (9 \times 3+7) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15048}{76923} := \frac{(15+04) \times 8}{7 \times (6 \times 9 \times 2+3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15078}{34692} := \frac{1+50 \times 7+8}{3 \times 4 \times 69-2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15087}{24396} := \frac{150-8 \times 7}{2+4 \times 39-6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15087}{49632} := \frac{1+50+8 \times 7}{4 \times 96-32}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15093}{46827} := \frac{1+50-9-3}{46+82-7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15093}{62478} := \frac{1+(5+09) \times 3}{6 \times (24+7)-8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15093}{87462} := \frac{150+9-3}{(8+74 \times 6) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15096}{47328} := \frac{15+096}{4 \times (7^3-2^8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15096}{83472} := \frac{1+(5+09) \times 6}{(8-3) \times 47 \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15207}{64938} := \frac{15+207}{6+4+938}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15236}{84970} := \frac{1+5 \times (2-3+6)}{84-9+70}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15246}{90387} := \frac{1+5-2+4+6}{9 \times 03+8 \times 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15246}{90783} := \frac{1-5+2+4 \times 6}{(9+07) \times 8+3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15264}{97308} := \frac{1-5+2 \times (6+4)}{97-3+08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15276}{30894} := \frac{1^5 \times (2^7+6)}{3 \times 089+4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15276}{83904} := \frac{1 \times 5^2+7 \times 6}{(83+9) \times 04}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15280}{63794} := \frac{1 \times 5 \times 2 \times 8+0}{6+(3+79) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15296}{47083} := \frac{(1+5-2)^{9-6}}{4 \times 70-83}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{24867} := \frac{(1+5) \times 30+9}{(2+48) \times 6+7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{27468} := \frac{(1+53) \times 09}{2 \times (74 \times 6-8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{27648} := \frac{(1+5^3) \times 09}{2^7 \times (6-4) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{27864} := \frac{(1+5) \times 30+9}{(2+78+6) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{48276} := \frac{(1+5) \times 30+9}{4+8 \times (-2+76)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{62748} := \frac{(1+5+30) \times 9}{(6 \times 27+4) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{67284} := \frac{(1+5+3) \times 09}{(6 \times 7+2) \times 8+4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{78624} := \frac{(1+53) \times 09}{78 \times (6^2-4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15327}{80496} := \frac{1 \times 5 \times (3+2^7)}{80 \times (49-6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15360}{49728} := \frac{(1^5+3) \times 60}{49+728}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15368}{49720} := \frac{1+5 \times (36+8)}{4-9+720}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15390}{26784} := \frac{15+3 \times 90}{2 \times (6+7 \times 8) \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15390}{27648} := \frac{15+3 \times 90}{2^{7+6+4-8}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15390}{27864} := \frac{15+3 \times 90}{2^{7+8-6+4}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15390}{46872} := \frac{15+3 \times 90}{(4+6) \times 87-2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15390}{68742} := \frac{(15-3) \times 90}{6+(8+7^4) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15390}{72846} := \frac{1^{53} \times 90}{(7+2 \times 8 \times 4) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15390}{82764} := \frac{1^{53} \times 90}{(8+2 \times 7)^{6-4}}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15390}{84672} := \frac{15+3 \times 90}{(8+4 \times 6) \times 7^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15402}{78369} := \frac{1-5+40-2}{7 \times (8+3 \times 6) - 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15407}{38269} := \frac{1+54+07}{3+82+69}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{15408}{29376} := \frac{1^5+40 \times 8}{(2+93+7) \times 6}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{15408}{97632} := \frac{1^5 + 40 \times 8}{9 \times (76 \times 3 - 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15792}{43680} := \frac{(1+5) \times 7 \times 9 - 2}{(4+3+6) \times 80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15928}{47603} := \frac{1+59+28}{47+6^{03}}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15423}{60897} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 4 \times 23}{60 \times 8 - 97}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15792}{60348} := \frac{15 \times 7 + 9 - 2}{60 \times (3+4) + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15930}{27864} := \frac{1 \times 59 \times 30}{(2+7) \times 86 \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15423}{78069} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 4 \times 23}{7 \times 80 - 69}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15834}{62790} := \frac{1 \times 5 \times (8-3) + 4}{6^2 + 79 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15930}{48672} := \frac{1 \times 59 \times 30}{4 \times 8 \times (6+7)^2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15480}{69273} := \frac{(1^5 + 4) \times 8 + 0}{6 \times 9 + 2^7 - 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15840}{29376} := \frac{1+58-4+0}{2 \times (93-7 \times 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15930}{76482} := \frac{1 \times 59 \times 30}{7 \times (6^4 - 82)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15480}{93267} := \frac{(1^5 + 4) \times 8 + 0}{9 \times (32-6) + 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15840}{32967} := \frac{15 \times 8 \times 4 + 0}{32 + 967}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15930}{84672} := \frac{1 \times 59 \times 30}{8 \times 4 \times 6 \times 7^2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15496}{70328} := \frac{1-5-(4-9) \times 6}{70+3 \times 2 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15840}{67392} := \frac{1+58-4+0}{6 \times (7 \times 3 + 9 \times 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15934}{62708} := \frac{(1 \times 59 + 3) \times 4}{(-6+2^7) \times 08}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15624}{79380} := \frac{(1+5 \times 6) \times (2+4)}{7+938+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15862}{37904} := \frac{1+(5+8) \times 6-2}{(37+9) \times 04}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15936}{80427} := \frac{1-5+9 \times 36}{804 \times 2+7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15674}{83902} := \frac{1-5+6 \times 7-4}{8-(3-90) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15873}{62049} := \frac{(1+58+7) \times 3}{(6+20 \times 4) \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15960}{78432} := \frac{1^5+9+60}{78 \times 4+32}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15678}{20943} := \frac{1 \times 56 + 78}{20 \times 9 - 4 + 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15876}{23490} := \frac{1+5+876}{(2 \times 3)^4 + 9 - 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15974}{28036} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 97 - 4}{2 \times (80 + 3) + 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15687}{30429} := \frac{1+(5+6) \times (8+7)}{304+2 \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15876}{23940} := \frac{1^5+8 \times 7+6}{2-3 \times (9-40)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15984}{26307} := \frac{1+59-8-4}{2 \times (6+30) + 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15698}{20374} := \frac{1 \times 5 \times 6 + 9 + 8}{20+37+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15876}{30942} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 87 + 6}{3+094 \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15984}{26730} := \frac{(1+5) \times 98 + 4}{(26+7) \times 30}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15703}{42896} := \frac{15+70-3}{4^2 \times 8 + 96}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15876}{49302} := \frac{(15-8) \times 7 \times 6}{4+9+30^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15984}{27306} := \frac{(15+9) \times (8-4)}{2^7+30+6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15708}{49623} := \frac{1+5 \times 7+08}{4+(9+6^2) \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15879}{36024} := \frac{1-5-8+79}{(36+02) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15984}{36720} := \frac{1-5+9+8 \times 4}{36+7^2+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15708}{63294} := \frac{1+5+70-8}{6 \times (3+2) \times 9+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15879}{46230} := \frac{158-79}{46 \times (2+3) + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15984}{37260} := \frac{(1+5) \times 98 + 4}{(3 \times 7 + 2) \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15708}{92463} := \frac{1+5 \times 7+08}{9-2+4 \times 63}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15879}{64320} := \frac{158-79}{64 \times (3+2) + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15984}{60273} := \frac{1+59+84}{60 \times (2+7) + 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15729}{60348} := \frac{(1-5) \times 7 \times (2-9)}{(60+34) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15903}{48267} := \frac{1+59+0-3}{(4 \times 8 - 2) \times 6 - 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15984}{62370} := \frac{(1+5) \times 98 + 4}{(6^2 - 3) \times 70}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15732}{40986} := \frac{1-5+7 \times 3 \times 2}{4+09+86}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15903}{64728} := \frac{1+59+0-3}{(6 \times 4 + 7 - 2) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16029}{87543} := \frac{1 \times 6 - 02 + 9}{8+75-4 \times 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15738}{94062} := \frac{1+(5 \times (7+3) - 8)}{9+4 \times 062}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15903}{82764} := \frac{1+5+90-3}{(8+2 \times 7)^{6-4}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16038}{27459} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times (03+8)}{2 \times (7+45) + 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{15792}{34608} := \frac{(15+79) \times 2}{(3+4) \times 60 - 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15908}{34276} := \frac{1 \times 590 - 8}{(3^4 + 2^7) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16038}{47952} := \frac{160+38}{4 \times (79-5) \times 2}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{16038}{74925} := \frac{160+38}{(7 \times 4+9) \times 25}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16425}{30879} := \frac{1-6+4^2 \times 5}{3 \times (08 \times 7-9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16758}{32490} := \frac{1-(6-7-5) \times 8}{3-2+4+90}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16038}{79542} := \frac{1+60+38}{7+9 \times 54-2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16472}{58930} := \frac{1-6+(4+7)^2}{5 \times 89-30}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16758}{92340} := \frac{(1+6)^{7-5} \times 8}{9 \times 2 \times 3 \times 40}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16038}{95742} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times (03+8)}{(9+5) \times 7 \times 4+2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16482}{95073} := \frac{(1 \times 6-4) \times 82}{950-7+3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16830}{95472} := \frac{168-3+0}{9 \times (5+47) \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16059}{37842} := \frac{160-59}{(3+7 \times 8) \times 4+2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16490}{53278} := \frac{1-6+490}{(5 \times 3)^2 \times 7-8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16835}{24790} := \frac{1-(6-8 \times 3) \times 5}{2 \times (4+7 \times 9)+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16059}{47382} := \frac{160-59}{4 \times 73+8-2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16497}{20358} := \frac{1^6-4+97}{2 \times (0 \times 3+58)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16872}{39045} := \frac{16+8 \times 72}{(3 \times 90+4) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16074}{82935} := \frac{160+7 \times 4}{(8+2 \times 93) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16497}{25803} := \frac{1+(6-4+9) \times 7}{2+5 \times 8 \times 03}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16905}{87423} := \frac{(16-9) \times 05}{8 \times (7+4^2)-3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16092}{35748} := \frac{160-9-2}{3^5+(7+4) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16524}{39780} := \frac{(1 \times 6-5+2)^4}{3 \times (9+7 \times 8)+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16940}{72358} := \frac{16 \times 9-4+0}{(7^2-3) \times (5+8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16245}{83790} := \frac{1+6 \times (2-4+5)}{8+(3+7) \times 9+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16524}{79380} := \frac{1-6+52+4}{7 \times (9 \times 3+8)+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16947}{35280} := \frac{1 \times 69 \times 4-7}{35 \times 2 \times 8+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16254}{39087} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times (25-4)}{390-87}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16524}{97308} := \frac{1+6+52+4}{9 \times 7+308}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16954}{78023} := \frac{1+6+95-4}{7 \times 8^{02}+3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16254}{79380} := \frac{1+62+5^4}{7 \times (9-3) \times 80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16530}{48792} := \frac{1-6+5 \times 30}{4 \times (8+7+92)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16974}{30258} := \frac{1+6+(9-7)^4}{3-02+5 \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16275}{39804} := \frac{(1+6-2) \times 7 \times 5}{(3 \times 9+80) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16548}{70392} := \frac{165+4 \times 8}{70 \times (3+9)-2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16974}{32085} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 9+7 \times 4}{(3+20+8) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16302}{87945} := \frac{16+30 \times 2}{(87-9+4) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16578}{39042} := \frac{1+6 \times (-5+7 \times 8)}{3+90 \times 4 \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16974}{53820} := \frac{1+6^{9-7}+4}{5 \times (3 \times 8+2)+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16340}{97825} := \frac{1-6+3^4+0}{(9+7 \times 8) \times (2+5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16578}{49302} := \frac{1+6 \times (-5+7 \times 8)}{4+9+30^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16975}{83420} := \frac{(1+69) \times (7-5)}{8+34 \times 20}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16359}{78204} := \frac{1+(-6+3 \times 5) \times 9}{(78+20) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16587}{20349} := \frac{1 \times 6+(5+8) \times 7}{2^{03+4}-9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16983}{25704} := \frac{1+6 \times 98+3}{2^5 \times 7 \times 04}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16380}{59724} := \frac{(1-6) \times 3+80}{5+(9+7^2) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16587}{93024} := \frac{1 \times 6+(5+8) \times 7}{9 \times 30 \times 2+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17024}{93856} := \frac{1 \times 70+2+4}{(93-8) \times 5-6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16380}{74529} := \frac{1^{63} \times 80}{7 \times (45-2+9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16704}{38592} := \frac{1^6+7 \times 04}{3+8 \times (-5+9) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17028}{43956} := \frac{1+7 \times (-02+8)}{4^3-9+56}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16380}{92547} := \frac{1^{63} \times 80}{9^2 \times 5+47}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16704}{52983} := \frac{1+67-04}{5+2 \times 9 \times (8+3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17028}{93456} := \frac{1+7 \times (-02+8)}{9+3+4 \times 56}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16380}{94752} := \frac{(1-6) \times 3+80}{9 \times (47-5)-2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16704}{89523} := \frac{1+67-04}{(8+9-5 \times 2)^3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17034}{68952} := \frac{(170-3) \times 4}{(6 \times 8+9-5)^2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{16380}{97524} := \frac{(1-6) \times 3+80}{9 \times (7 \times 5+2 \times 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{16724}{50398} := \frac{1 \times 6+72-4}{5^{03}+98}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17043}{62985} := \frac{1 \times 70-4+3}{(6 \times 2-9) \times 85}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{17052}{34986} := \frac{1 \times 70 \times 5 - 2}{(3^4 + 9) \times 8 - 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17286}{59340} := \frac{1 \times 7 + (2 + 8) \times 6}{5 \times (9 - 3 + 40)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17496}{23085} := \frac{1 - 7 + 49 \times 6}{2 \times (30 + 8) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17052}{83496} := \frac{17 \times 05 + 2}{(8 + (3 + 4) \times 9) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17290}{53846} := \frac{17 + 2 \times 9 + 0}{5^3 + 8 \times (4 - 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17496}{50328} := \frac{17 + 4^{9-6}}{(5 \times 03)^2 + 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17052}{89436} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times (05 + 2)}{8 - 9 + 43 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17324}{69580} := \frac{1 - 7 + 32 \times 4}{6 \times 95 - 80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17496}{52380} := \frac{(1 \times 7 - 4) \times 9 \times 6}{5 + 2 \times 3 \times 80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17064}{83592} := \frac{1 + 706 + 4}{(8 + 35) \times 9^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17325}{40986} := \frac{1 \times 7^3 + 2 + 5}{(40 + 98) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17496}{82350} := \frac{(1 + 7 + 4) \times 9 \times 6}{(8^2 - 3) \times 50}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17064}{93528} := \frac{1 + 706 + 4}{9 + 3^5 \times 2 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17325}{86940} := \frac{(1 + 7 + 3) \times 2 \times 5}{(8 - 6)^9 + 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17520}{86943} := \frac{(1 + 7) \times 5 \times 2 + 0}{8 \times (6 \times 9 - 4) - 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17068}{43925} := \frac{(1 + 7) \times 068}{(4 + 3 \times 92) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17325}{98406} := \frac{1^7 \times 3 \times 25}{9 \times (8 + 40) - 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17523}{40986} := \frac{1 + 7 \times 5 + 23}{(40 - 9 - 8) \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17085}{26934} := \frac{1^7 \times 085}{2 + (6 + 9 \times 3) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17328}{69540} := \frac{(1 \times 7 \times 3 - 2) \times 8}{6 \times 95 + 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17523}{84960} := \frac{(1 + 7 + 5^2) \times 3}{8 \times 4 \times (9 + 6) + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17085}{29346} := \frac{1^7 \times 085}{2 + (9 - 3) \times 4 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17340}{62985} := \frac{17 \times 3 \times 4 + 0}{6 \times 2 + 9^{8-5}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17540}{69283} := \frac{1^7 \times 5 \times 4 + 0}{69 + 2 \times (8 - 3)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17205}{46398} := \frac{(1 + 7) \times 20 - 5}{4 - 6 \times (3 - 9 \times 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17340}{69258} := \frac{1 + 7^3 - 4 + 0}{6 \times 9 \times 25 + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17563}{84920} := \frac{1 - 7 \times 5 + 6^3}{(8 + 4 \times 9) \times 20}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17250}{36984} := \frac{(1 + 7^2) \times 5 + 0}{(36 + 98) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17385}{20496} := \frac{1 \times 7 + 3 + 85}{2^{04} + 96}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17582}{30694} := \frac{1 \times 75 - 8 \times 2}{3 + 06 + 94}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17250}{39468} := \frac{(1 + 7 \times 2) \times 50}{3 \times (94 \times 6 + 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17385}{29640} := \frac{1 + (7 - 3 + 8) \times 5}{2 \times 9 \times 6 - 4 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17589}{40326} := \frac{(1 + 7) \times 5 - 8 + 9}{40 + 3^2 \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17253}{89460} := \frac{1 + 7^2 \times 5 - 3}{(8 + 9 + 4) \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17402}{63958} := \frac{1 + 74 + 02}{6 + 3 \times 95 - 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17639}{28450} := \frac{1 + 7 + 63 - 9}{(2 \times 8 + 4) \times 5 + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17264}{83590} := \frac{(172 - 6) \times 4}{(8 - 3)^5 + 90}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17420}{39865} := \frac{(1 + 7) \times 4 + 20}{(3 \times 9 - 8) \times 6 + 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17640}{59283} := \frac{(1^7 + 6) \times 40}{59 \times 2 \times 8 - 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17280}{34695} := \frac{(1 + 7) \times 2 \times 8 + 0}{(34 - 6) \times 9 + 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17420}{63985} := \frac{(1 + 7) \times 4 + 20}{6 \times (39 - 8) + 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17640}{89523} := \frac{1 - 7 + 6 + 40}{(8 + 95) \times 2 - 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17280}{34965} := \frac{1^7 \times 2^8 + 0}{(3 + 4) \times (9 + 65)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17430}{25896} := \frac{1 + 74 + 30}{2 + 58 + 96}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17649}{23850} := \frac{1 - 7 - 6 + 49}{2^3 - 8 + 50}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17280}{64395} := \frac{1^7 \times 2^8 + 0}{6 \times (4^3 + 95)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17458}{26390} := \frac{1 \times 7 - 4 + 5 \times 8}{26 + 39 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17649}{28305} := \frac{(17 - 6) \times 4 + 9}{2 + 83 + 0 \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17280}{94536} := \frac{(1 + 7 \times 2) \times 80}{9^4 - 5 + 3 + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17458}{69230} := \frac{1 \times 74 + 5 + 8}{69 \times (2 + 3) + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17802}{34569} := \frac{1 + 7 + 80 - 2}{34 \times 5 + 6 - 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17284}{35960} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 2^8 - 4}{(3 + 59) \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17493}{65280} := \frac{(1 - 7 + 4 + 9)^3}{(6 + 5 \times 2) \times 80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17820}{35964} := \frac{1 + 7 \times 8 - 2 + 0}{3 \times 5 \times 9 - 6 \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17284}{95360} := \frac{1^7 + 2^8 + 4}{(9 + 5 \times 3) \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17496}{20385} := \frac{(1 + 7 + 4) \times 9 \times 6}{20 \times 38 - 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17820}{64395} := \frac{(1 + 7) \times 8 - 20}{6 \times 4 + 3 \times 9 \times 5}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{17820}{93456} := \frac{17+8+20}{9+3+4 \times 56}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17952}{34680} := \frac{(1+7+9+5) \times 2}{3-4+6+80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18207}{35496} := \frac{(1+8 \times 2) \times 07}{3^5+4-9-6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17820}{94365} := \frac{178-2+0}{943-6-5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17980}{45632} := \frac{17 \times 9-8+0}{4 \times (5 \times 6 \times 3+2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18207}{96543} := \frac{(1+8 \times 2) \times 07}{9-6+5^4+3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17850}{26439} := \frac{1^7 \times 850}{2+6^4-39}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17982}{36450} := \frac{1+79-8+2}{3 \times (6+4) \times 5+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18239}{70564} := \frac{1-(8+2) \times (3-9)}{(70-5-6) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17850}{49623} := \frac{1+7-8+50}{4+(9+6^2) \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17982}{45360} := \frac{17+982}{(45-3) \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18240}{35796} := \frac{18^2-4+0}{3+5^{7-9+6}}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17850}{62394} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 850}{62+(3+9)^4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17982}{53460} := \frac{1+(7-9+8)^2}{5 \times 34-60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18240}{93765} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 2^4+0}{9^3-76+5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17850}{63294} := \frac{1^7 \times 850}{6+32 \times 94}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{17985}{32046} := \frac{(1-7+9+8) \times 5}{(3+20) \times 4+6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18256}{37490} := \frac{1^{82} \times 56}{3 \times 7+4+90}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17850}{92463} := \frac{1+7-8+50}{9-2+4 \times 63}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18023}{49765} := \frac{1 \times 8^{02}+3}{(4-9+7 \times 6) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18270}{34965} := \frac{1+8^2-7+0}{3 \times (4 \times 9+6-5)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17854}{30962} := \frac{178-5 \times 4}{30 \times 9+6-2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18032}{94576} := \frac{(18+03)^2}{9+4 \times 576}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18270}{45936} := \frac{1 \times 8+27+0}{4^5-936}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17856}{94023} := \frac{1+7 \times (8-5+6)}{9 \times 40-23}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18042}{36957} := \frac{180+4+2}{369+5+7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18270}{46935} := \frac{1+8^2-7+0}{4 \times 6 \times (9-3)+5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17860}{39245} := \frac{1+7+8+60}{3 \times 9 \times (2+4)+5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18054}{29736} := \frac{1 \times 8+05+4}{2 \times ((9-7)^3+6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18297}{40356} := \frac{1 \times 8+2+97}{4 \times (03+56)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17928}{30456} := \frac{1-7+9^2+8}{3 \times 045+6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18063}{27945} := \frac{1+(80-6) \times 3}{(2+7 \times 9+4) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18304}{67925} := \frac{1 \times 8^3+0 \times 4}{(6 \times 7 \times 9+2) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17928}{34056} := \frac{1+(7+9)^2-8}{(3+40) \times (5+6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18063}{45927} := \frac{1+(80-6) \times 3}{(4+59) \times (2+7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18304}{92576} := \frac{18 \times (30-4)}{9 \times (257+6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17928}{63504} := \frac{1-7+9^2+8}{6 \times (3+50-4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18063}{47952} := \frac{1+(80-6) \times 3}{4 \times (79-5) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18354}{20769} := \frac{(1 \times 8 \times 3-5) \times 4}{20 \times 7-6 \times 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17936}{54280} := \frac{(1 \times 7+9+3) \times 6}{5^4-280}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18063}{49572} := \frac{1+(80-6) \times 3}{4 \times (9+(5+7)^2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18354}{69027} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 35-4}{6 \times (90 \times 2-7)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17940}{28635} := \frac{1+7 \times 9+40}{2 \times (8 \times 6+35)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18063}{74925} := \frac{1+(80-6) \times 3}{(7 \times 4+9) \times 25}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18354}{76209} := \frac{1+(8-3) \times (5+4)}{7 \times (6+20)+9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17940}{32568} := \frac{1+(7+9) \times 4+0}{3 \times (2+5) \times 6-8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18075}{29643} := \frac{(1 \times 8+07) \times 5}{2 \times (9+6) \times 4+3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18360}{45792} := \frac{1+8 \times 3+60}{4 \times (5 \times 7+9 \times 2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17940}{63825} := \frac{1+7 \times 9+40}{((6+3) \times 8+2) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18096}{52374} := \frac{1 \times 8+096}{5+2 \times 37 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18360}{47952} := \frac{1+8 \times 3+60}{4-7+9 \times 5^2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17940}{83265} := \frac{1+7 \times (9+4)+0}{8 \times 3^2 \times 6-5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18096}{73254} := \frac{1 \times 8+096}{(7 \times 3)^2-5 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18360}{75429} := \frac{(1+8-3) \times 60}{7 \times 5 \times 42+9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17945}{23680} := \frac{1+7+94-5}{2^3 \times 6+80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18204}{75369} := \frac{1 \times 82 \times 04}{7 \times (5^3+69)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18360}{79254} := \frac{1^{83} \times 60}{7 \times (9+2^5-4)}$

$$\begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{18432}{76950} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 4^{3+2}}{76 \times 9 \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18450}{29736} := \frac{1 + (8-4)^5 + 0}{2 \times (97 + 3^6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18450}{37296} := \frac{1 + (8-4)^5 + 0}{37 \times (2 + 9 \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18450}{69372} := \frac{(1+8-4) \times 5 + 0}{6+9 \times (3+7) - 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18450}{92736} := \frac{1 + (8-4)^5 + 0}{(9-2) \times (7+3^6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18450}{93726} := \frac{1^8 \times 450}{(9+372) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18492}{36570} := \frac{(18+49) \times 2}{3 \times 65 + 70} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18495}{20736} := \frac{1 \times 8^4 + 9 + 5}{2^{07} \times 36} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18506}{47239} := \frac{1 \times 8 + 5 \times 06}{(4+7) \times 2^3 + 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18526}{97340} := \frac{1 \times 85 - 26}{9 + 7 \times (3+40)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18532}{70964} := \frac{(1 \times 85 - 3) \times 2}{70 \times 9 - 6 + 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18573}{60249} := \frac{1+8 \times (-5+7+3)}{60 \times 2 + 4 + 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18576}{23490} := \frac{18 \times 57 + 6}{(2 \times 3)^4 + 9 - 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18576}{49032} := \frac{185 - 7 - 6}{4 + 90 \times (3+2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18603}{25974} := \frac{(1-8+60) \times 3}{25 \times 9 - 7 + 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18603}{45279} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 60 - 3}{4 + 5 + 2^7 \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18603}{49725} := \frac{(1-8+60) \times 3}{(4+9+72) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18603}{74529} := \frac{(1-8+60) \times 3}{7 \times (4 \times 5^2 - 9)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18630}{24975} := \frac{18 \times 6 + 30}{(2 - (4-9) \times 7) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18630}{42795} := \frac{18 \times 6 + 30}{4 - 2 + 7 \times 9 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18630}{49275} := \frac{18 \times 6 + 30}{(4-9) \times (2-75)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18630}{79245} := \frac{18 \times 6 + 30}{7 \times 9^2 + 4 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18630}{92475} := \frac{18 \times 6 + 30}{(9 \times 2^4 - 7) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18630}{95427} := \frac{1+86+3+0}{9 \times (54-2) - 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18639}{42750} := \frac{18+6^3 \times 9}{(4+2) \times 750} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18639}{54207} := \frac{1-8+6^3+9}{5^4+2+07} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18643}{57920} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 64 + 3}{5 \times (7+9) \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18643}{70952} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 64 + 3}{70 \times (9+5) \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18690}{73425} := \frac{1^8 + 69 + 0}{(7+3 \times 4^2) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18703}{26945} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 7 + 03}{2 - 6 + 94 - 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18703}{92564} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 7 + 03}{9 \times (2 + 5 \times 6) + 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18705}{24639} := \frac{1 \times 87 \times 05}{2 + 4 + 63 \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18706}{49352} := \frac{1 + 87 + 06}{4 \times ((9+3) \times 5 + 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18706}{52934} := \frac{1 + 87 + 06}{5 \times 2 \times 9 \times 3 - 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18720}{59436} := \frac{1 \times 8 + 72 + 0}{5 - 9 + 43 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18720}{94536} := \frac{1 - 8 + 7 + 20}{9 + 4 \times (5 + 3 \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18760}{29435} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times (7+60)}{29^{4+3-5}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18760}{43952} := \frac{1 - 8 + 7 \times 6 + 0}{(4+3+9) \times 5 + 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18763}{45290} := \frac{1 \times 87 \times (6-3)}{(4+5-2) \times 90} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18792}{30456} := \frac{18 - 7 + 9 \times 2}{3 + 04 \times (5+6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18792}{34560} := \frac{1 \times 87 \times 9 \times 2}{(3+45) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18792}{63504} := \frac{1+8+7 \times (9-2)}{6^3 - 5 \times 04} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18905}{47362} := \frac{1+89+05}{4 \times (7+3) \times 6 - 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18907}{35624} := \frac{1+8 \times (90+7)}{3^5 \times 6 + 2 + 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18927}{35640} := \frac{1+(8+92) \times 7}{3 \times (5+6) \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18927}{36450} := \frac{1+(8+92) \times 7}{(3+6 \times 4) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18942}{35670} := \frac{189+42}{3 \times 5 + 6 \times 70} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18942}{75306} := \frac{1 \times 8 - 9 + 42}{7 + 5 \times 30 + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18952}{40376} := \frac{1 \times 89 + 5 - 2}{40 \times 3 + 76} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18954}{20736} := \frac{1+8 \times (9+5) + 4}{2 + 07 \times 3 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18954}{26730} := \frac{(1+8 \times 9 + 5) \times 4}{2 + 6 \times 73 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18954}{37206} := \frac{1+8-9+54}{(3+7)^2 + 0 + 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18957}{60342} := \frac{1+8 \times 9 + 5 - 7}{(60-3) \times 4 - 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18963}{40572} := \frac{1-8+96-3}{40 + (5+7)^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18964}{70253} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times (9+6-4)}{70 + 2^{5+3}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18972}{46053} := \frac{(1+8+9) \times 7 - 2}{4 + 60 \times 5 - 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{18972}{60543} := \frac{1+8 \times 9 - 7 + 2}{(60-5) \times 4 - 3} \end{array}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{19024}{35786} := \frac{1+9^{0^2} \times 4}{3 \times 5 + 7 \times 86}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19206}{45738} := \frac{(1+9) \times 20 - 6}{457 - 3 + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19380}{25764} := \frac{1 \times 93 - 8 + 0}{(2+5) \times 7 + 64}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19024}{85376} := \frac{1+9^{-0^2+4}}{8 + (53+7) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19206}{83754} := \frac{(1+9) \times 20 - 6}{837 + 5 + 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19380}{62475} := \frac{19 \times 3 \times 8 + 0}{6 \times (2+47) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19032}{56784} := \frac{1+9^{0^3} + 2}{56 \times (7+8 \times 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19256}{70384} := \frac{1+9+25-6}{70+3 \times (8+4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19380}{74256} := \frac{1^9 \times 380}{(7 \times 4 - 2) \times 56}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19035}{24786} := \frac{(1+90+3) \times 5}{2 \times (4 \times 78 - 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19275}{34680} := \frac{(1+9) \times 2^7 + 5}{34 \times 68 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19456}{70832} := \frac{(1+9 \times 4 - 5) \times 6}{708 - 3^2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19035}{24867} := \frac{1-9+03^5}{(2+48) \times 6 + 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19275}{40863} := \frac{1-9-2+7 \times 5}{4 \times (08+6) - 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19467}{23058} := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 4 + 67}{2 \times (3+058)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19035}{27864} := \frac{1-9+03^5}{(2+78+6) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19275}{43860} := \frac{(1+9) \times 2^7 + 5}{43 \times (8+60)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19467}{28350} := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 4 + 67}{(2+8) \times 3 \times 5 + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19035}{28674} := \frac{1-9+03^5}{(2+8 \times 6) \times 7 + 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19278}{36045} := \frac{(19-2) \times 7 \times 8}{(360-4) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19467}{80325} := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 4 + 67}{(80+3+2) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19035}{48276} := \frac{1-9+03^5}{4-8 \times (2-76)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19278}{36450} := \frac{(19-2) \times 7 \times 8}{(3+6) \times 4 \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19468}{37052} := \frac{1+94+6-8}{3 \times (7+052)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19035}{78246} := \frac{(1+90+3) \times 5}{7 \times (8-2) \times 46}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19278}{45603} := \frac{(19-2) \times 7 \times 8}{4 \times (560+3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19485}{20736} := \frac{(1+9 \times 48) \times 5}{2^{0^7} \times 3 \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19046}{37825} := \frac{190+4 \times 6}{(3 \times 7 + 8^2) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19305}{46728} := \frac{(1 \times 9 + 30) \times 5}{4 \times (6+7 \times 2 \times 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19485}{72063} := \frac{(1+9 \times 48) \times 5}{7+20^{6-3}}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19046}{75328} := \frac{1+90+4-6}{(7+5+32) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19305}{46827} := \frac{(1 \times 9 + 30) \times 5}{468 - 2 + 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19502}{84376} := \frac{(1 \times 9 + 5)^{0^2}}{8 \times (4^3 + 7 \times 6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19053}{64728} := \frac{1+9 \times (05+3)}{(6-4)^7 \times 2 - 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19305}{62478} := \frac{(-1+9+3) \times 05}{6 \times (24+7) - 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19530}{64728} := \frac{1+9-5+30}{6 \times (4+7 \times 2) + 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19074}{28356} := \frac{190-7+4}{2 \times (83+56)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19305}{72468} := \frac{(1+9+3) \times 05}{7 \times (2+4) \times 6 - 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19536}{87024} := \frac{1+9^{5-3} + 6}{8 \times 7^{-0^2+4}}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19074}{65382} := \frac{190-7+4}{65 + (3 \times 8)^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19305}{76824} := \frac{(1 \times 9 + 30) \times 5}{768 + 2 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19570}{28634} := \frac{1^9 \times 570}{2 - (8 - 6^3) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19074}{82365} := \frac{19-0+7-4}{(8+2+3+6) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19305}{82764} := \frac{(1 \times 9 + 30) \times 5}{8^2 \times (7+6) + 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19584}{67320} := \frac{(1-9+5 \times 8) \times 4}{6 \times 73 + 2 + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19075}{36842} := \frac{(1+9) \times 07 \times 5}{(3 \times 6 + 8)^{4-2}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19305}{86427} := \frac{(1 \times 9 + 30) \times 5}{864 + 2 + 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19584}{76032} := \frac{1+9-5+8+4}{7+60-3+2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19075}{62348} := \frac{(1+9) \times 07 \times 5}{(62+3^4) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19320}{45678} := \frac{(1+9-3) \times 20}{4+5 \times 67-8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19602}{35478} := \frac{1^9 + 60 \times 2}{3 + (5 \times 4 + 7) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19085}{24637} := \frac{(19-08) \times 5}{2 \times 46 - 3 \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19320}{54786} := \frac{(1+9-3) \times 20}{5+4 \times 7 \times (8+6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19602}{37584} := \frac{1^9 + 60 \times 2}{((3+7) \times 5 + 8) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19203}{64875} := \frac{19+203}{(6-4+8) \times 75}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19320}{86457} := \frac{(1^9+3) \times 20}{8+(6+4) \times 5 \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19602}{43758} := \frac{1+96+02}{4+3 \times 75-8}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{19602}{53784} := \frac{1^9 + 60 \times 2}{(5 + 37) \times 8 - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19764}{58320} := \frac{1 + 9 \times (7 + 6) + 4}{5 \times 8 \times 3^2 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20175}{86349} := \frac{(-2 \times 01 + 7) \times 5}{8 + 63 + 4 \times 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19602}{73458} := \frac{1 + 96 + 02}{7^3 + 4 \times 5 + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19765}{30284} := \frac{1 + 9 \times (7 + 6) \times 5}{30^2 + 8 - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20176}{35984} := \frac{20 + 1 + 76}{3 \times 59 - 8 + 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19608}{34572} := \frac{19 \times (6 - 0 \times 8)}{(34 - 5) \times 7 - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19782}{45360} := \frac{1^9 + 78 \times 2}{4 \times 5 \times 3 \times 6 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20176}{58394} := \frac{2 + 017 \times 6}{5 + (83 - 9) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19620}{85347} := \frac{1^{96} \times 20}{8 - 5 + 3 \times 4 \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19824}{30576} := \frac{1 + 9 \times (8 - 2) + 4}{3 \times 05 + 76}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20178}{36594} := \frac{2 + 01 + 7 \times 8}{3 \times 6 - 5 + 94}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19642}{35807} := \frac{1 \times 964 + 2}{3 \times (580 + 7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19824}{50736} := \frac{19 \times (8 - 2) + 4}{50 + 7 \times 36}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20178}{63954} := \frac{2 + 01 + 7 \times 8}{6^3 - 9 - 5 \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19647}{28305} := \frac{(19 - 6) \times 4 + 7}{2 + 83 - 0 \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19832}{54760} := \frac{1 + (9 + 8 \times 3) \times 2}{5 - (4 - 7) \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20196}{34578} := \frac{(2 + 01 \times 9) \times 6}{(3 + 4) \times 5 + 78}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19647}{82305} := \frac{19 - 6 \times (4 - 7)}{(8 + 23) \times 05}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19834}{67520} := \frac{1 \times (9 + 8) \times 3 - 4}{(6 + 7 + 5) \times 20}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20196}{75438} := \frac{20 - 1 + 9 + 6}{7 \times (5 + 4 \times 3) + 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19683}{24570} := \frac{(1^{96} + 8)^3}{(2 \times 4 + 5) \times 70}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19836}{27405} := \frac{(1 + 9 \times 8 + 3) \times 6}{2 \times 7 \times (40 + 5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20196}{83457} := \frac{20 - (1 - 9) \times 6}{8 + (34 + 5) \times 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19683}{57024} := \frac{(1 \times 9 - 6)^{8-3}}{5 \times 70 \times 2 + 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19836}{47025} := \frac{1 \times 98 + 3 \times 6}{(4 + 7) \times 025}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20196}{85374} := \frac{-2 \times 01 + 9 + 6}{8 + 5 \times (3 \times 7 - 4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19683}{74250} := \frac{(1^{96} + 8)^3}{(7 + 4) \times 250}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19836}{75240} := \frac{19 - 8 + 3 \times 6}{7 \times 5 \times 2 + 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20358}{46719} := \frac{2 \times 03 \times (5 + 8)}{46 + 7 \times 19}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19706}{25384} := \frac{1 + 9 \times (7 + 06)}{(2 \times 5 \times 3 + 8) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19837}{64052} := \frac{1 + 9 \times 8 + 3 + 7}{6 \times (40 + 5) - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20358}{96174} := \frac{2 + 035 - 8}{9 \times (6 + 1) + 74}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19728}{34056} := \frac{19 \times 7 \times 2 + 8}{(3 + 40) \times (5 + 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19845}{20736} := \frac{1 \times 98 \times 45}{2^{07} \times 36}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20358}{97614} := \frac{2 \times 03 \times (5 + 8)}{9 \times 7 \times 6 \times 1 - 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19728}{34560} := \frac{19 + 7^2 \times 8}{(3 + 4 + 5) \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19845}{32760} := \frac{1 \times 9 \times (8 + 4 \times 5)}{32 \times (7 + 6) + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20367}{51894} := \frac{20 + 3 \times 6 \times 7}{(5 - 1 + 89) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19750}{34286} := \frac{1^9 \times 750}{3 \times (428 + 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19845}{67230} := \frac{(19 - 8) \times 4 + 5}{(6 + 7)^2 - 3 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20367}{95418} := \frac{2 \times 03 + 67}{9 \times (5 + 41 - 8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19758}{60342} := \frac{1 \times 9 + 7 + 58}{(60 - 3) \times 4 - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20139}{48657} := \frac{20 + 13 \times 9}{4 \times (86 - 5) + 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20376}{59184} := \frac{203 \times 7 - 6}{5 + 9 + 1 \times 8^4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19760}{25384} := \frac{(19 + 7) \times 60}{2 \times 5^3 \times 8 + 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20163}{59784} := \frac{20 \times (1 + 6) + 3}{((5 + 9) \times 7 + 8) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20398}{65471} := \frac{2 \times (039 - 8)}{6 \times (5 + 4 \times 7) + 1}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19762}{34850} := \frac{19 \times 76 + 2}{(3 + 48) \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20163}{87945} := \frac{20 - 1 + 6^3}{(8 - 7)^9 + 4^5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20451}{78693} := \frac{20 \times 4 \times 5 + 1}{7 + (8 - 6)^9 \times 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19764}{32805} := \frac{(19 + 7 \times 6) \times 4}{3 + 2 + 80 \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20169}{47385} := \frac{20 + (1 + 6) \times 9}{(4 - 7 \times (3 - 8)) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20493}{57816} := \frac{(20 + 49) \times 3}{578 + 1 \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19764}{53802} := \frac{1 \times 9 + 7 + 6 - 4}{(5 \times 3 - 8^{02})}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20174}{85936} := \frac{2 + 01 + 74}{8 \times (5 + (9 - 3) \times 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20493}{61578} := \frac{(20 + 49) \times 3}{6 \times 15 \times 7 - 8}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{20493}{67518} := \frac{(20+49) \times 3}{675-1+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20916}{35784} := \frac{20 \times (9-1) + 6}{3 \times (5+7) \times 8-4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21573}{49068} := \frac{2 \times (15 \times 7 - 3)}{(4+9 \times 06) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20493}{81675} := \frac{2 \times 04 \times 9 - 3}{(8 \times 1 \times 6 + 7) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20916}{73584} := \frac{20 \times (9-1) + 6}{(7+3) \times 58+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21583}{70964} := \frac{215-8 \times 3}{70 \times 9 - 6 + 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20493}{87561} := \frac{2+04 \times 9 \times 3}{8+7 \times (5+61)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20943}{75816} := \frac{20 \times 9 - 4 + 3}{(7+5) \times (8+1) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21584}{39760} := \frac{2-1+5+8 \times 4}{3-9+76+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20536}{41978} := \frac{2^{05} + 36}{4+1 \times 9 \times (7+8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20943}{85176} := \frac{20 \times 9 - 4 + 3}{8 \times (5 \times 17 + 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21630}{47895} := \frac{2^{1+6} - 30}{4 \times 78 - 95}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20541}{93687} := \frac{(2+05) \times 41}{93 \times (6+8) + 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20958}{63714} := \frac{2^{09} - 5 - 8}{6^3 \times 7 + 1 + 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21658}{93704} := \frac{2+(1+6+5) \times 8}{(9-3) \times 70 + 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20574}{83916} := \frac{2+05^{7-4}}{(83-9) \times (1+6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21045}{98637} := \frac{210+4 \times 5}{98 \times (6 \times 3 - 7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21736}{45980} := \frac{2-1+7+3 \times 6}{4+59-8+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20587}{63491} := \frac{2^{05} + 87}{6-3+4 \times 91}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21063}{54978} := \frac{2 \times 10 + 6^3}{5^4 + 9 \times (7-8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21798}{45360} := \frac{2+179-8}{4 \times 5 \times 3 \times 6+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20654}{31879} := \frac{2 \times (065+4)}{3 \times 1 \times (8+7 \times 9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21087}{45369} := \frac{2 \times (10+8 \times 7)}{4 \times (5-3+69)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21856}{70349} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times (8+5) + 6}{70-3+4 \times 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20683}{49751} := \frac{20+6+8+3}{4+9+75+1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21358}{79640} := \frac{2-1+3^5-8}{(7+9+6) \times 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21945}{36708} := \frac{2-1+9+45}{36+7 \times 08}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20691}{45738} := \frac{2+06 \times 9+1}{45+73+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21360}{85974} := \frac{2 \times 1^3 \times 60}{8 \times 59+7+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21973}{65408} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7+3}{(-6+54) \times 08}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20736}{41895} := \frac{2^{07} \times 3 \times 6}{(41+8) \times 95}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21384}{70956} := \frac{2+1 \times 38 \times 4}{7-0+9 \times 56}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21978}{34056} := \frac{2 \times (1+97 \times 8)}{(3+40) \times 56}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20736}{48195} := \frac{2^{0 \times 7 + 3 + 6}}{(4+81) \times (9+5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21385}{40796} := \frac{(2+1 \times 3+8) \times 5}{4 \times 07+96}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21978}{34650} := \frac{2 \times (1+97 \times 8)}{(3+46) \times 50}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20736}{51984} := \frac{(20+7-3) \times 6}{5 \times (1+9 \times 8) - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21386}{90457} := \frac{(2+1)^3 \times 8+6}{904+5 \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21978}{35046} := \frac{2 \times 19+7-8}{35-0+4 \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20736}{59184} := \frac{(20+7-3) \times 6}{5 \times (91-8) - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21465}{97308} := \frac{(2-1-4+6) \times 5}{(9-7) \times 30+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21978}{35640} := \frac{21 \times 9 - 78}{3 \times (56+4) + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20736}{91854} := \frac{2+07 \times 3 \times 6}{9 \times (1+8+54)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21470}{63958} := \frac{21+4+70}{6+3 \times 95-8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21978}{43065} := \frac{2 \times (1+9) \times 7+8}{(4^3-06) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20817}{35964} := \frac{2^{08} + 1^7}{(3 \times 5 + 96) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21473}{68950} := \frac{(2+14) \times 7-3}{(6-8+9) \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21978}{65340} := \frac{21 \times 9 - 78}{6 \times (5 \times 3 + 40)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20817}{65934} := \frac{2^{08} + 1^7}{6 \times 5 \times 9 \times 3 + 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21483}{56079} := \frac{2 \times (1-4) + 83}{5 \times 6 \times 07 - 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21987}{45360} := \frac{219 \times 8 - 7}{4 \times 5 \times 3 \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20851}{69743} := \frac{2-0+85 \times 1}{69+74 \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21507}{68943} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 50 + 7}{68 \times (9-4) + 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23058}{91476} := \frac{2 \times (3-0+58)}{9-1+476}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20895}{46137} := \frac{(208-9) \times 5}{4+6+1 \times 3^7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21509}{78364} := \frac{21+50 \times 9}{78 \times (3 \times 6+4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23085}{41796} := \frac{230-8 \times 5}{4 \times (1+79+6)}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{23085}{47196} := \frac{2+3-0+8 \times 5}{4-7-1+96}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23607}{59841} := \frac{2 \times 3 \times 6+07}{(5+9) \times 8-4+1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24057}{91368} := \frac{2+40+57}{9-1+368}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23091}{86457} := \frac{2 \times (30-9)+1}{(8+6+4+5) \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23650}{48719} := \frac{2 \times 3-6+50}{(4+8) \times 7+19}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24058}{93617} := \frac{2+4-0+5 \times 8}{9 \times 3 \times 6+17}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23108}{76954} := \frac{2+(3+10) \times 8}{7 \times (6+9 \times 5)-4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23698}{75140} := \frac{236-9 \times 8}{(7+5+1) \times 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24068}{79315} := \frac{2+40-6+8}{(7-9+31) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23157}{94860} := \frac{2 \times 3 \times 15-7}{(9-4) \times (8+60)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23716}{59048} := \frac{(2+3) \times 7 \times (1+6)}{5 \times (90+4 \times 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24087}{36519} := \frac{2 \times (4-0+8)+7}{3-6+5 \times (1+9)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23157}{98604} := \frac{2+3+1 \times 57}{(9 \times 8-6) \times 04}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23718}{49560} := \frac{2 \times 37+1-8}{4 \times (95-60)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24150}{63798} := \frac{(24-1) \times 50}{6+379 \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23175}{80649} := \frac{2+3^{17} \times 5}{80-6+4+9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23718}{54069} := \frac{2 \times (3+7 \times 1 \times 8)}{5 \times 40+69}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24153}{79680} := \frac{2 \times 41+5 \times 3}{(7-9+6) \times 80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23409}{57681} := \frac{2 \times 3^4-09}{(5+7 \times 6) \times 8+1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23751}{49068} := \frac{2+3^7-5 \times 1}{(4+90) \times 6 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24190}{36875} := \frac{2 \times 41 \times 9+0}{3 \times (68+7) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23409}{86751} := \frac{2-3 \times (4-09)}{8 \times (6+7-5)-1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23790}{54168} := \frac{2 \times 37-9+0}{5 \times 4 \times (1+6)+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24198}{36075} := \frac{2+(4-1) \times 9 \times 8}{360-7 \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23409}{87516} := \frac{2 \times 3^4-09}{8 \times 7+516}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23790}{65148} := \frac{2 \times 37-9+0}{6 \times 5+148}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24309}{61758} := \frac{2-4+30+9}{6+(-1+7+5) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23415}{86970} := \frac{2 \times (3-4+15)}{8+6 \times (9+7)-0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23814}{67095} := \frac{238+14}{6+709-5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24381}{60795} := \frac{2+4+381}{60 \times (7+9)+5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23478}{69015} := \frac{2+3 \times 4 \times (7+8)}{6 \times 90 \times 1-5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23840}{57961} := \frac{(2+38) \times 4+0}{5 \times 79-6 \times 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24381}{67095} := \frac{2+4+3^{8-1}}{670 \times 9+5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23490}{61857} := \frac{2 \times (3^4+9)+0}{6 \times (1+85-7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23851}{46970} := \frac{23 \times 85 \times 1}{(46+9) \times 70}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24381}{95760} := \frac{2 \times 43 \times (8+1)}{(9-5) \times 760}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23490}{71568} := \frac{(2 \times 3)^4+9-0}{7 \times 1 \times 568}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23856}{97104} := \frac{(2+3+8) \times 5+6}{9+7 \times 10 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24381}{96750} := \frac{2+43+81}{(9-6+7) \times 50}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23517}{96480} := \frac{235-1^7}{(9-6) \times 4 \times 80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23870}{41695} := \frac{2 \times (3+8) \times 7+0}{4+(-1+6 \times 9) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24570}{69381} := \frac{(2-4+5) \times 70}{6 \times 9 \times (3+8)-1}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23540}{69871} := \frac{(2 \times 3+5) \times 40}{(6+9) \times 87+1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23871}{49056} := \frac{2 \times (38+71)}{4+90 \times 5-6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24570}{86931} := \frac{(2-4+5) \times 70}{8+6+9^3 \times 1}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23541}{86907} := \frac{2^3+5^{4-1}}{8+69 \times 07}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23871}{56940} := \frac{23+87-1}{(56+9) \times 4+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24597}{83106} := \frac{2 \times 459-7}{(8^3+1) \times 06}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23598}{47610} := \frac{2+3^5-9-8}{(4+7 \times 6) \times 10}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23874}{96015} := \frac{2 \times (3-8+74)}{9 \times 60+15}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24651}{38907} := \frac{2 \times (46-5)+1}{3+8 \times (9+07)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23598}{61047} := \frac{2^{3+5}-9 \times 8}{6+10 \times 47}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23985}{61470} := \frac{(2+39) \times (8+5)}{6^{1 \times 4}+70}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24705}{86193} := \frac{(-2+47) \times 05}{8 \times (6+1)+9^3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23607}{58194} := \frac{2 \times 3 \times 6+07}{5+8-1+94}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24017}{86359} := \frac{2 \times (40+1 \times 7)}{86+3^5+9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{24735}{60819} := \frac{247+3+5}{608+19}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{24759}{30618} := \frac{2 \times (4 \times 7 \times 5 - 9)}{3 \times 06 \times 18}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25017}{86349} := \frac{2^5 - 01^7}{8 + 63 + 4 \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25641}{90783} := \frac{2 + 5 + 6 \times (4 + 1)}{(9 + 07) \times 8 + 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24769}{80135} := \frac{2 \times 4 \times (7 - 6) + 9}{(8 + 01 \times 3) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25086}{34917} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 08 - 6}{3 \times 4 \times (9 - 1) + 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25647}{89301} := \frac{(25 - 6) \times 4 + 7}{(8 + 9)^{3-01}}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24786}{31059} := \frac{24 + 786}{(3 + 1)^{05} - 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25098}{41736} := \frac{250 - 9 \times 8}{41 \times 7 + 3 + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25704}{31689} := \frac{(2^5 + 70) \times 4}{(3 - 1)^6 \times 8 - 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24786}{31590} := \frac{2 + 47 + 8 - 6}{31 \times 5 - 90}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25137}{86940} := \frac{(25 + 13) \times 7}{(8 + 6 + 9) \times 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25704}{63189} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 70 - 4}{(6^3 - 1) \times 8 - 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24786}{39015} := \frac{2^4 \times 78 - 6}{(390 + 1) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25160}{97384} := \frac{25 + 1 \times 60}{9 + (7 + 3) \times 8 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25704}{83916} := \frac{(2 \times 5 + 7) \times 04}{8 \times 3 \times 9 \times 1 + 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24790}{36815} := \frac{2 \times (4 + 7 \times 9) + 0}{3 \times 68 \times 1 - 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25164}{37890} := \frac{2 \times 51 + 6^4}{3^7 + 8 - 90}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25704}{96831} := \frac{(2^5 + 70) \times 4}{(9 - 6) \times 8^3 + 1}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24795}{31806} := \frac{(24 + 7 \times 9) \times 5}{3 \times (180 + 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25194}{76038} := \frac{25 \times 1 \times 9 - 4}{7 + 60 \times (3 + 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25709}{48136} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 70) - 9}{4 \times (8 + 1 \times 3) \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24795}{36801} := \frac{(2 \times 4 - 7) \times 95}{3 \times (6 \times 8 - 01)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25197}{80364} := \frac{(25 + 1) \times 9 - 7}{80 \times (3 + 6) + 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25740}{69381} := \frac{2^5 \times 7 - 4 + 0}{6 \times 9 \times (3 + 8) - 1}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24831}{56079} := \frac{2 + 4 + 83 \times 1}{5 \times 6 \times 07 - 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25317}{49068} := \frac{(2^5 \times 3 + 1) \times 7}{(4 + 90) \times (6 + 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25740}{86931} := \frac{2^5 \times 7 - 4 + 0}{8 + 6 + 9^3 \times 1}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24857}{31906} := \frac{2 \times (4 \times 8 + 5) - 7}{3 - 1 + 90 - 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25317}{68904} := \frac{2 \times (53 - 1) - 7}{6 \times (8 + 9 \times 04)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25803}{64719} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 8 \times 03}{(6 + 4 \times 7 \times 1) \times 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24875}{36019} := \frac{2 \times 4 \times (8 + 7) + 5}{3 \times 60 + 1^9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25380}{64719} := \frac{2 \times (5 - 3 + 8) + 0}{6 \times (4 + 7 - 1) - 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25806}{73491} := \frac{2^5 + 8 + 06}{(7 + 3) \times (4 + 9) + 1}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24897}{31605} := \frac{2 \times (4 + 89) + 7}{(3 + 1) \times 60 + 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25384}{61790} := \frac{(2 + 5 + 3) \times 8 - 4}{6 + 179 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25830}{74169} := \frac{2^5 + 8 + 30}{7 \times (4 + 1) \times 6 - 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24956}{70831} := \frac{2 \times (4 \times 95 - 6)}{708 \times 3 - 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25389}{40176} := \frac{2 \times (5 - 3 + 89)}{(40 + 1 + 7) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25896}{47310} := \frac{(2 + 5) \times (8 + 96)}{(4 + 7)^3 - 1 + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24957}{36108} := \frac{2 + 4 + 95 - 7}{(3 \times 6 - 1) \times 08}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25398}{47061} := \frac{2 \times (5 \times (3 + 9) + 8)}{4 \times (70 - 6 - 1)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25916}{73408} := \frac{25 \times 9 - 16}{(-7 + 3^4) \times 08}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24957}{36801} := \frac{2 - (4 - 9) \times 5 \times 7}{3 \times (6 + 80 + 1)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25410}{93786} := \frac{2 + 54 - 1 + 0}{9 \times 3 \times 7 + 8 + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25917}{30846} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 9 \times 17}{30 \times 8 - 46}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24957}{68103} := \frac{2 - (4 - 9) \times 5 \times 7}{6 \times (8 \times 10) + 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25410}{98736} := \frac{(25 - 4) \times 10}{9 \times (87 + 3) + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25917}{40863} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 9 \times 17}{40 \times 8 - 63}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24960}{31785} := \frac{2 \times 4^{9-6} + 0}{3 \times 1 \times 7 \times 8 - 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25413}{80967} := \frac{254 + 1 + 3}{809 + 6 + 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25974}{83106} := \frac{2 \times (5 \times 97 - 4)}{(8^3 + 1) \times 06}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24975}{61830} := \frac{(2 - (4 - 9) \times 7) \times 5}{61 \times 8 - 30}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25608}{73914} := \frac{2 \times (5 \times 6 - 08)}{7 + 3 \times (9 + 1) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25986}{47031} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 9 \times 8 - 6)}{4^{7-03} + 1}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24986}{70153} := \frac{2 + 4 \times (9 - 8) \times 6}{70 + 1 + 5 - 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25608}{91374} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 6 - 08}{9 + 1 \times 37 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{26015}{97438} := \frac{2 \times (60 - 1 \times 5)}{(97 \times 4) + (3 \times 8)}$

▶ $\frac{26019}{37485} := \frac{2 \times (60 - 1^9)}{3 + 7 + 4 \times 8 \times 5}$	▶ $\frac{26910}{87354} := \frac{26 \times (9 + 1) + 0}{8 \times 7 \times 3 \times 5 + 4}$	▶ $\frac{27189}{36450} := \frac{(2^7 - 1) \times 8 - 9}{(3 + 6 \times 4) \times 50}$
▶ $\frac{26047}{31598} := \frac{2^6 + 04 - 7}{3 - 1^5 + 9 \times 8}$	▶ $\frac{26937}{50184} := \frac{2 \times (69 - 3 + 7)}{(50 + 18) \times 4}$	▶ $\frac{27189}{40356} := \frac{2 \times 71 + 8 + 9}{4 \times (03 + 56)}$
▶ $\frac{26104}{59738} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 104}{(5 + 9 + 7^3) \times 8}$	▶ $\frac{26937}{84501} := \frac{2 \times (69 - 3 + 7)}{8 + 450 \times 1}$	▶ $\frac{27189}{43605} := \frac{2^{7+1^8} + 9}{(4 + 3) \times 60 + 5}$
▶ $\frac{26145}{79380} := \frac{2 \times (61 \times 4 + 5)}{7 \times 9 \times 3 \times 8 + 0}$	▶ $\frac{26937}{85410} := \frac{2^6 + 93 + 7}{(8 + 5) \times 4 \times 10}$	▶ $\frac{27195}{64380} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 1 \times (9 + 5)}{6 \times 4^3 + 80}$
▶ $\frac{26190}{38475} := \frac{2 \times (6 + 1 + 90)}{3 \times (8 + 4 + 7) \times 5}$	▶ $\frac{26970}{41385} := \frac{2 + 6 + 9 \times 70}{41 \times 3 \times 8 - 5}$	▶ $\frac{27195}{84360} := \frac{2 + 7 - (1 - 9) \times 5}{8 + 4 \times 36 + 0}$
▶ $\frac{26190}{43875} := \frac{2 \times (6 + 1 + 90)}{(4^3 + 8 - 7) \times 5}$	▶ $\frac{26973}{51840} := \frac{26 + 973}{(5 + 1) \times 8 \times 40}$	▶ $\frac{27306}{48951} := \frac{2^7 + 30 + 6}{4 \times 8 \times 9 + 5 + 1}$
▶ $\frac{26190}{48735} := \frac{2 \times (6 + 1 + 90)}{4 - 8 + 73 \times 5}$	▶ $\frac{26980}{37145} := \frac{(2 - 6) \times (9 - 80)}{371 + 4 \times 5}$	▶ $\frac{27306}{49815} := \frac{2 \times (7 + 30) \times 6}{4 - 9 + 815}$
▶ $\frac{26307}{51948} := \frac{2 \times (6 + 30) + 7}{(5 - 1 + 9) \times (4 + 8)}$	▶ $\frac{27018}{36594} := \frac{2 + 70 - 1 + 8}{3 \times 6 - 5 + 94}$	▶ $\frac{27354}{60819} := \frac{273 + 5 + 4}{608 + 19}$
▶ $\frac{26394}{57081} := \frac{2 \times (6 + 3) \times 9 + 4}{5 \times 70 + 8 + 1}$	▶ $\frac{27018}{56943} := \frac{2 \times (70 + 1 + 8)}{5 \times 69 - 4 \times 3}$	▶ $\frac{27360}{91485} := \frac{2 \times (7 + 3 + 6) + 0}{(9 + 1 + 4) \times 8 - 5}$
▶ $\frac{26491}{58370} := \frac{2^6 + 4 - 9 \times 1}{(5 + 8) \times (3 + 7) + 0}$	▶ $\frac{27018}{65493} := \frac{2 \times (70 + 1 + 8)}{6 + 5 + 4 \times 93}$	▶ $\frac{27391}{58604} := \frac{2 + 7 \times (3 + 9 \times 1)}{(5 \times 8 + 6) \times 04}$
▶ $\frac{26549}{30178} := \frac{265 + 4 + 9}{301 + 7 + 8}$	▶ $\frac{27051}{64389} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 05 + 1}{6 \times 43 - 89}$	▶ $\frac{27405}{81693} := \frac{2 \times (740 - 5)}{8 + 1 \times 6 \times 9^3}$
▶ $\frac{26574}{89301} := \frac{2 \times (6 + 5 \times 7) + 4}{(8 + 9)^{3-01}}$	▶ $\frac{27051}{83496} := \frac{2^{7-0 \times 5-1}}{8 \times (34 + 9 + 6)}$	▶ $\frac{27450}{86193} := \frac{(2 + 7 - 4) \times 50}{8 \times (6 + 1) + 9^3}$
▶ $\frac{26730}{84159} := \frac{(2 + 6 \times 7) \times 30}{8^4 + 1 + 59}$	▶ $\frac{27063}{45198} := \frac{2 + (70 - 6) \times 3}{4 - 5 \times (1 - 9) \times 8}$	▶ $\frac{27450}{91683} := \frac{(2 + 7 \times 4) \times 5 + 0}{9 \times (1 + 6) \times 8 - 3}$
▶ $\frac{26784}{35910} := \frac{2 \times (6 + 7 \times 8) \times 4}{35 \times (9 + 10)}$	▶ $\frac{27063}{51894} := \frac{2 + (70 - 6) \times 3}{(5 - 1 + 89) \times 4}$	▶ $\frac{27451}{86039} := \frac{27 + 4^{5-1}}{860 + 3 \times 9}$
▶ $\frac{26790}{31584} := \frac{2 \times 6 - 7 + 90}{(31 + 5 - 8) \times 4}$	▶ $\frac{27064}{89351} := \frac{270 + 6 - 4}{893 + 5 \times 1}$	▶ $\frac{27459}{30618} := \frac{2 \times (7 + 45) + 9}{3 \times 06 \times (-1 + 8)}$
▶ $\frac{26790}{35814} := \frac{2 \times 6 - 7 + 90}{3 \times (5 \times 8 + 1) + 4}$	▶ $\frac{27081}{46359} := \frac{2 + 7 \times 08 + 1}{4 \times (6 \times 3 + 5) + 9}$	▶ $\frac{27459}{83106} := \frac{(27 \times 4 + 5) \times 9}{(8^3 + 1) \times 06}$
▶ $\frac{26809}{37145} := \frac{2 \times 6 + 80 - 9}{(37 - 14) \times 5}$	▶ $\frac{27084}{53619} := \frac{2 \times (70 + 8 - 4)}{5 - 36 \times (1 - 9)}$	▶ $\frac{27485}{69310} := \frac{27 \times 4 - 85}{6 \times 9 + 3 + 1 + 0}$
▶ $\frac{26871}{35490} := \frac{2 \times (68 \times 7 + 1)}{35 \times 4 \times 9 + 0}$	▶ $\frac{27135}{89640} := \frac{(2 + 7 + 1)^3 + 5}{(89 - 6) \times 40}$	▶ $\frac{27495}{30186} := \frac{(2 \times 7 \times 4 - 9) \times 5}{3 \times 01 \times 86}$
▶ $\frac{26910}{58374} := \frac{2^6 - 9 + 10}{5 + 8 \times (3 \times 7 - 4)}$	▶ $\frac{27189}{35640} := \frac{(2^7 - 1) \times 8 - 9}{3 \times (5 + 6) \times 40}$	▶ $\frac{27495}{36801} := \frac{(2 + 7 \times 4 + 9) \times 5}{3 \times (6 + 80 + 1)}$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{27495}{38610} &:= \frac{2 + (7 + 49) \times 5}{386 + 10} & \blacktriangleright \frac{27891}{35640} &:= \frac{2^7 \times 8 + 9 \times 1}{3 \times (5 + 6) \times 40} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28350}{49167} &:= \frac{(2 + 8 - 3) \times 50}{4 + 9 \times 1 \times 67} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27495}{68103} &:= \frac{(2 + 7 \times 4 + 9) \times 5}{6 \times 8 \times 10 + 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{27891}{36450} &:= \frac{2^7 \times 8 + 9 \times 1}{(3 + 6 \times 4) \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28350}{69174} &:= \frac{2 \times (8 - 3) \times 5 + 0}{6 \times (9 - 1) + 74} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27501}{94863} &:= \frac{2 + 7^{5-01}}{9^4 + 8 \times 6^3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{27904}{35861} &:= \frac{(2 - 7 + 9)^{04}}{3^5 + 86 \times 1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28350}{69741} &:= \frac{2^{8-3} \times 50}{6 \times (9 + 7) \times 41} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27531}{64980} &:= \frac{2^7 \times 5 + 3 + 1}{(6 + 4 + 9) \times 80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{27918}{35046} &:= \frac{2 + 7 \times 9 - 18}{35 + 04 \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28350}{91476} &:= \frac{(2 + 8) \times 3 \times 5 + 0}{9 - 1 + 476} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27540}{81396} &:= \frac{(2 \times 7 - 5) \times 40}{8 \times (139 - 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{27918}{43065} &:= \frac{2 \times (7 + 91) - 8}{(4^3 - 06) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28356}{71094} &:= \frac{2 \times (83 + 56)}{710 - 9 - 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27594}{83160} &:= \frac{2 - 7 \times (5 - 9 \times 4)}{(8 + 3 \times 1) \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{27918}{65340} &:= \frac{2 \times (791 + 8)}{(6 + 5) \times 340} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28359}{41607} &:= \frac{2 \times 8 \times (3 + 5) + 9}{(4 - 1) \times (60 + 7)} \\ & & \blacktriangleright \frac{27936}{51840} &:= \frac{2 \times (7 + 93) - 6}{5 \times 18 \times 4 + 0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28359}{47610} &:= \frac{2^8 - (3 - 5) \times 9}{(4 + 7 \times 6) \times 10} \\ & & \blacktriangleright \frac{27945}{61830} &:= \frac{2 \times (7 + 94) + 5}{61 \times 8 - 30} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28379}{40651} &:= \frac{28 + 37 + 9}{40 + 65 + 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27648}{31590} &:= \frac{2^7 \times (6 - 4) \times 8}{(31 - 5) \times 90} & \blacktriangleright \frac{27945}{63180} &:= \frac{2 - (7 - 9) \times 45}{6^{3 \times 1} - 8 + 0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28431}{59670} &:= \frac{2 \times (84 - 3 \times 1)}{5 \times 9 \times 6 + 70} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27648}{35910} &:= \frac{2^{7+6+4-8}}{35 \times (9 + 10)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{27945}{83106} &:= \frac{(2 \times 7 + 9) \times 45}{(8^3 + 1) \times 06} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28461}{39750} &:= \frac{2 \times (84 + 6) - 1}{(3 + 9 - 7) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27654}{93018} &:= \frac{27 + 6 \times (5 - 4)}{93 + 018} & \blacktriangleright \frac{27965}{84130} &:= \frac{2 \times (7 \times 9 - 6) + 5}{8 \times 41 + 30} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28469}{70315} &:= \frac{2 + 8 + 4 + 69}{70 \times 3 \times 1 - 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27810}{34695} &:= \frac{27 \times 8 - 10}{(34 - 6) \times 9 + 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28013}{76954} &:= \frac{2^8 + 01^3}{7 + 695 + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28476}{90513} &:= \frac{2 + 8 - (4 - 7) \times 6}{90 - 5 + 1 + 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27819}{64053} &:= \frac{2 + 7 \times 8 \times (1 + 9)}{6^4 - 05 + 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28059}{36417} &:= \frac{280 - 5 \times 9}{3 \times 6 + 41 \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28560}{43197} &:= \frac{2 + (8 + 5) \times 6 + 0}{(4 \times 3 - 1)^{9-7}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27819}{65340} &:= \frac{2 + 7 \times 8 \times (1 + 9)}{(6 + 5) \times 3 \times 40} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28059}{73461} &:= \frac{2 \times (805 - 9)}{73 + 4^6 - 1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28710}{43956} &:= \frac{2 \times 87 \times 10}{(439 + 5) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27830}{56419} &:= \frac{2 + 78 + 30}{56 \times 4 - 1^9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28105}{73964} &:= \frac{2^8 \times 10 - 5}{(73 + 9)^{6-4}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28714}{50396} &:= \frac{28 + 7 + 14}{50 - (3 - 9) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27846}{31590} &:= \frac{(2 + 7 \times 8) \times 4 + 6}{3 \times 1^5 \times 90} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28106}{79534} &:= \frac{(2 + 8) \times 10 - 6}{7 \times (9 - 5 + 34)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28743}{90651} &:= \frac{287 - 4 + 3}{906 - 5 + 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27846}{39015} &:= \frac{2^7 + 8 + 46}{3 \times (90 - 1 \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28194}{36075} &:= \frac{2 + (8 - 1) \times 9 \times 4}{360 - 7 \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28764}{39015} &:= \frac{2 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6 + 4)}{3 \times (90 - 1 \times 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27860}{49153} &:= \frac{2 + 78 + 60}{(49 + 1) \times 5 - 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28194}{50673} &:= \frac{2^{8-1} + 94}{50 + 6 + 7^3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28905}{41736} &:= \frac{2 \times 8 \times 90 - 5}{4 \times ((1 + 7)^3 + 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27864}{35910} &:= \frac{2^{7+8-6} + 4}{35 \times (9 + 10)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28350}{41796} &:= \frac{(2 + 8 - 3) \times 50}{4 + (1 + 7)^{9-6}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{28907}{41356} &:= \frac{2 \times 8 \times 9 - 07}{4 \times (1 + (3 + 5) \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27864}{93150} &:= \frac{2 + 78 + 6^4}{(93 - 1) \times 50} & & & & \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{28914}{35076} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 9 \times (1 + 4)}{3 - 5 + 076}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29103}{75864} := \frac{2 + 9 \times 10 - 3}{(7 - 5)^8 - 6 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29376}{84150} := \frac{2^{9+3-7} \times 6}{(8 + 4 - 1) \times 50}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{28914}{75603} := \frac{2^8 - 9 + 1 - 4}{7 \times 5 + 603}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29103}{85674} := \frac{2 + 9 \times 10 - 3}{(8 + 5 \times 6) \times 7 - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29403}{57816} := \frac{294 + 03}{578 + 1 \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{28917}{40635} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times (9 + 1) - 7}{4 + 06^3 - 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29106}{57834} := \frac{(2 + 9) \times (1 + 06)}{57 + 8 \times 3 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29403}{61578} := \frac{294 + 03}{6 \times 15 \times 7 - 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{28917}{45360} := \frac{289 + 17}{4 \times (5 - 3) \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29106}{73458} := \frac{2 \times (9 \times 10 - 6)}{(73 - 4 \times 5) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29410}{87365} := \frac{2 - 9 + 41 + 0}{87 + 3 + 6 + 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{28917}{46053} := \frac{2 + 8 + 9 + 1 + 7}{46 + 0 \times 5 - 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29106}{83457} := \frac{2 + 9 \times 10 + 6}{8 + (34 + 5) \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29415}{60738} := \frac{2 \times (94 + 1) - 5}{60 \times 7 - 38}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{28917}{46305} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times (9 + 1) - 7}{(46 + 3) \times 05}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29160}{38475} := \frac{2 + 9 + 1 + 60}{(3 \times (8 - 4) + 7) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29430}{81675} := \frac{2 \times 94 + 30}{(8 \times 16 - 7) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{28917}{53460} := \frac{2 \times (8 + 9 \times 1) \times 7}{5^3 \times 4 - 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29160}{53784} := \frac{(29 + 1) \times 6 + 0}{(5 + 37) \times 8 - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29547}{36180} := \frac{2 \times ((9 + 5) \times 4 - 7)}{3 \times (6 - 1) \times 8 + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{28945}{60371} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 94 - 5}{6 + 03 \times 71}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29160}{57834} := \frac{(2 + 9 - 1) \times 60}{5 \times (78 \times 3 + 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29578}{63014} := \frac{2 \times (9 - 5) + 7 + 8}{63 - 014}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{28946}{70315} := \frac{2 + 8 \times (94 - 6)}{7^{03} \times 1 \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29160}{73845} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 1 \times 60}{7^3 \times 8 - 4 - 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29601}{73485} := \frac{2^9 + 60 \times 1}{(73 \times 4 - 8) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{28950}{61374} := \frac{(2 + 8 - 9) \times 50}{6 \times 13 + 7 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29160}{84375} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 1 \times 60}{((8 - 4) \times 3 - 7)^5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29640}{31785} := \frac{2 \times 96 - 40}{3 \times 1 \times 7 \times 8 - 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{28967}{40135} := \frac{2 - 8 + 96 - 7}{40 \times 1 \times 3 - 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29187}{53406} := \frac{2 \times (9 + 18) - 7}{5 + 3^4 + 0 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29640}{73815} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 6 - 4 + 0}{7 \times (38 - 1^5)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{28971}{36540} := \frac{(2 + 8 \times 9) \times (7 - 1)}{(3 + 6 + 5) \times 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29304}{51876} := \frac{2 - 9 + 3^{04}}{5 \times (18 + 7) + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29645}{38710} := \frac{2 \times (9 \times 6 + 4) + 5}{3 \times 8 \times 7 - 10}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{28975}{34160} := \frac{(2 + 8)^{9-7} - 5}{(3 + 4) \times 16 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29304}{57816} := \frac{2 + 9 + 30 - 4}{5 - 7 + 81 - 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29680}{57134} := \frac{(2 + 9 - 6) \times 8 + 0}{5 + 71 - 3 + 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{29013}{78546} := \frac{2^9 \times 01 - 3}{7^{8-5} \times 4 + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29308}{71546} := \frac{29 - 3 + 08}{7 \times (15 - 4) + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29714}{83056} := \frac{2 + 9^{7-1-4}}{8 \times (30 + 5 - 6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{29016}{43758} := \frac{2^9 - 016}{4 \times 37 \times 5 + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29346}{70518} := \frac{2 \times 9 + 3 + 46}{7 \times (05 + 18)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29718}{36504} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 7 + 1^8}{3 \times (6 + 50 - 4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{29016}{75348} := \frac{2^9 - 016}{((7 - 5) \times 3)^4 - 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29367}{51480} := \frac{293 - 6 \times 7}{(51 + 4) \times 8 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29718}{65403} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 71 - 8}{65 \times (40 + 3)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{29058}{71643} := \frac{2 \times 9 + 05 \times 8}{7 \times (16 + 4) + 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29370}{65148} := \frac{2 \times 9 + 37 - 0}{6 \times (5 + 14) + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29748}{61305} := \frac{2 + 9 \times (74 + 8)}{61 \times (30 - 5)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{29078}{31465} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 07 + 8}{(31 + 4 - 6) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29376}{40851} := \frac{2^{9-3} \times (7 - 6)}{4 + 085 \times 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29750}{81634} := \frac{2^9 - 7 - 5 + 0}{(8 - 1^6)^3 \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{29078}{45136} := \frac{2 + 9 + 07 \times 8}{4 \times (5 \times (1 + 3) + 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29376}{58140} := \frac{2 \times 93 - 7 \times 6}{5 + ((8 - 1) \times 40)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{29754}{36018} := \frac{2 + 9 + 7 + 5 - 4}{3 \times (6 - 01) + 8}$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29754}{36801} := \frac{2 \times (9 + (7+5) \times 4)}{3 \times (6 \times 8 - 01)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30195}{46728} := \frac{30 \times (1+9) + 5}{4 \times (6+7 \times 2 \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30492}{61578} := \frac{(30+4) \times 9 + 2}{6 \times 15 \times 7 - 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29754}{83106} := \frac{29 \times (7+5-4)}{8 \times 3^{10-6}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30195}{46827} := \frac{30 \times (1+9) + 5}{468 - 2 + 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30498}{51267} := \frac{(30-4) \times (9+8)}{5^{1+2} \times 6 - 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29754}{86130} := \frac{2+9+7+5-4}{86-1-30} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30195}{76824} := \frac{30 \times (1+9) + 5}{768+2 \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30618}{52974} := \frac{306+1+8}{5+2^9+7 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29785}{41630} := \frac{2^9 - 7 + 8 + 5}{4 \times (1+6 \times 30)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30195}{82764} := \frac{30 \times (1+9) + 5}{8^2 \times (7+6) + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30618}{59724} := \frac{(3+06) \times (1+8)}{5-9 \times (7-24)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29830}{76145} := \frac{(2+9) \times (8+30)}{7 \times 6 + 1 + 4^5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30195}{86427} := \frac{30 \times (1+9) + 5}{864+2+7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30618}{72954} := \frac{(3+06) \times (1+8)}{7+2 \times 95-4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29835}{40716} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times (8-3) - 5}{4+07 \times 16} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30257}{86941} := \frac{30+(2+5) \times 7}{(8 \times 6+9) \times 4-1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30618}{74592} := \frac{3^{06^{18}}}{(7-4) \times 592} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29835}{41067} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times (8-3) - 5}{4+106+7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30258}{97416} := \frac{3+0-2+5 \times 8}{97+41-6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30618}{79542} := \frac{30 \times 6 + 1 + 8}{7+9 \times 54-2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29835}{61047} := \frac{2 \times (98-3) + 5}{(61-04) \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30264}{51798} := \frac{3 \times 026 \times 4}{517+9+8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30618}{94752} := \frac{3^{06^{18}}}{94 \times (7+5) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29835}{61074} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times (8-3) - 5}{6 \times (1+07 \times 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30267}{54891} := \frac{3+(02+6) \times 7}{(5 \times 4-8) \times 9-1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30618}{95742} := \frac{3 \times 06 \times (-1+8)}{(9+5) \times 7 \times 4+2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29835}{67014} := \frac{2 \times (98-3) + 5}{6 \times (70-1+4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30267}{85491} := \frac{3 \times (02^6-7)}{8+5 \times (4+91)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30619}{47528} := \frac{30 \times (6+1) - 9}{4+7 \times (52-8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29845}{67310} := \frac{2 \times (9+8+4) + 5}{6+(7+3) \times 10} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30294}{51867} := \frac{3 \times (02 \times 9+4)}{5 \times (18+6) - 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30621}{84597} := \frac{30 \times 6 - 2 - 1}{8-4+5 \times 97} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29850}{36417} := \frac{2+98-50}{3 \times 6 \times (4-1) + 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30294}{57618} := \frac{(30 \times 2 - 9) \times 4}{5 \times 76 \times 1 + 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30624}{98571} := \frac{(30-6) \times 2 \times 4}{(98+5) \times (7-1)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29853}{40176} := \frac{29 \times 8 - 5^3}{4 \times (-01+7) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30294}{65178} := \frac{3 \times (02 \times 9+4)}{65-1+78} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30687}{49215} := \frac{3-06+8 \times 7}{4+9^{2^{15}}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30128}{49765} := \frac{(3+01) \times 28}{(4-9+7 \times 6) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30294}{81675} := \frac{3 \times (-02+9 \times 4)}{(8 \times 1 \times 6+7) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30694}{57812} := \frac{3+06+94}{((5+7) \times 8+1) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30167}{84592} := \frac{30+1 \times 67}{8 \times (45-9-2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30429}{86751} := \frac{304+2 \times 9}{867+51} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30721}{58469} := \frac{3+07+21}{5 \times (8-4+6) + 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30178}{69524} := \frac{3 \times (01+78)}{6 \times 95-24} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30456}{71928} := \frac{3+04 \times (5+6)}{7 \times (19-2) - 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30794}{86152} := \frac{30+79 \times 4}{8 \times (6+1 \times 5)^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30186}{49725} := \frac{3 \times 01 \times 86}{(4+9+72) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30472}{59186} := \frac{3+047+2}{5+9+1+86} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30798}{54162} := \frac{3-0+7 \times 9-8}{5 \times (4+16) + 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30186}{74529} := \frac{3 \times 01 \times 86}{7 \times (4 \times 5^2 - 9)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30492}{51876} := \frac{(3+04) \times (9+2)}{5 \times (18+7) + 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30814}{67592} := \frac{3-0+(8-1) \times 4}{6+7+5 \times (9+2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30195}{42768} := \frac{30 \times (1+9) + 5}{(4-2+7) \times 6 \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30492}{57816} := \frac{(30+4) \times 9 + 2}{578+1 \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30846}{79152} := \frac{308+4+6}{791+5^2}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{30879}{51246} &:= \frac{3 \times (08 \times 7 - 9)}{5 \times 12 \times 4 - 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31407}{92568} &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 4 + 07}{(9 + 2 \times (5 - 6)) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31758}{46029} &:= \frac{(3 - 1) \times 75 + 8}{4 \times 60 - 2 - 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{30879}{62415} &:= \frac{3 \times (08 \times 7 - 9)}{(62 - 4 - 1) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31590}{42768} &:= \frac{31 \times 5 - 90}{4 \times (2 \times 7 + 6) + 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31768}{59204} &:= \frac{3 - 1 \times 7 + 6 \times 8}{5 + 9^2 - 04} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{30912}{56784} &:= \frac{3 + 091 - 2}{(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8) + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31590}{47268} &:= \frac{3 \times 1^5 \times 90}{472 - 68} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31790}{65824} &:= \frac{3 - 1 - 7 + 90}{6 \times 5 \times (8 - 2) - 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{30942}{57186} &:= \frac{3 + 094 \times 2}{5 \times 71 - 8 + 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31590}{47628} &:= \frac{31 \times 5 - 90}{(47 + 6) \times 2 - 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31806}{59427} &:= \frac{3 - 1 + 80 - 6}{5 + 9 \times 4^2 - 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{30942}{75168} &:= \frac{3 + 094 \times 2}{(75 + 1) \times 6 + 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31590}{76284} &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5 \times 9 - 0}{7 \times 6 + 284} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31806}{75924} &:= \frac{31 - 8 \times 0 \times 6}{7 - 5 + 9 \times 2 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{30942}{87156} &:= \frac{3 + 094 \times 2}{8 \times 71 - 5 \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31608}{94752} &:= \frac{3^{1+6} + 08}{94 \times 7 \times 5 \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31824}{57096} &:= \frac{((3 + 1) \times 8)^2 - 4}{5 \times (70 - 9) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{30958}{41726} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 \times 9 + 5) + 8}{4 - 1 - 7 \times (2 - 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31620}{89745} &:= \frac{3 \times 16 + 20}{8 + ((9 + 7 \times 4) \times 5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31842}{57096} &:= \frac{3 + (1 + 8 + 4) \times 2}{5 - 7 - 0 + 9 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{30962}{41785} &:= \frac{30 \times (9 + 6) + 2}{41 \times (7 + 8) - 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31650}{97482} &:= \frac{31 - 6 + 50}{9 + 7 \times 4 \times 8 - 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31842}{79056} &:= \frac{3 + (1 + 8 + 4) \times 2}{7 + 9 - 0 + 56} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{30972}{65148} &:= \frac{30 \times (9 - 7) - 2}{6 \times (5 + 14) + 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31652}{87904} &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 65 - 2}{8 \times 7 \times 9 + 04} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31842}{96075} &:= \frac{(3 + 1 \times 84) \times 2}{(9 + 6) \times 07 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{31065}{98427} &:= \frac{(3 + 10 + 6) \times 5}{(9 - 8 + 42) \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31689}{70245} &:= \frac{(3 - 1)^6 \times 8 - 9}{70 \times 2^4 - 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31856}{74029} &:= \frac{318 \times 5 - 6}{(7 + 402) \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{31075}{49268} &:= \frac{310 - 7 \times 5}{4 \times 92 + 68} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31689}{72450} &:= \frac{(3 - 1)^6 \times 8 - 9}{(7 + 2^4) \times 50} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31902}{67485} &:= \frac{(3 + 1 + 9) \times 02}{6 + 7 \times (4 + 8 - 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{31076}{42958} &:= \frac{(3 + 1) \times 07 + 6}{4 - (2 - 9) \times 5 + 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31689}{74025} &:= \frac{(3 - 1)^6 \times 8 - 9}{(7 + 40) \times 25} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31920}{56784} &:= \frac{3 + 1 \times 92 + 0}{(5 + 6) \times (7 + 8) + 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{31240}{86975} &:= \frac{312 + 40}{(8 + 6)^{9-7} \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31692}{45870} &:= \frac{(3 + 1 + 6 + 9) \times 2}{4 - 5 + 8 \times 7 + 0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31928}{45760} &:= \frac{3 + 19 \times 2 \times 8}{4 \times 5 + 7 \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{31248}{57960} &:= \frac{31 \times (2 - 4 + 8)}{5 \times (7 \times 9 + 6) + 0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31692}{50874} &:= \frac{(3 + 1 + 6 + 9) \times 2}{50 + 8 + 7 - 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31968}{72504} &:= \frac{(3 - 1)^9 - 68}{7 + 250 \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{31248}{59706} &:= \frac{3 \times (1 + 2 + 4) \times 8}{5 \times 9 \times 7 + 06} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31724}{58960} &:= \frac{3^{1 \times 7} - 24}{(58 + 9) \times 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{32015}{49876} &:= \frac{3 \times (20 - 1) \times 5}{4 \times (98 + 7 + 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{31248}{60795} &:= \frac{31 \times (24 - 8)}{60 \times (7 + 9) + 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31725}{60489} &:= \frac{3 \times (1 + 7 \times 2^5)}{6^{-04+8} - 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{32016}{47589} &:= \frac{(3 + 20) \times 16}{475 + 8 \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{31248}{69750} &:= \frac{31 \times 2^4 + 8}{(6 + 9) \times 75 - 0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31752}{46980} &:= \frac{(3 \times 17 + 5)^2}{(4 + 6 \times 9) \times 80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{32016}{54897} &:= \frac{(3 + 20) \times 16}{5^4 + 8 - 9 + 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{31248}{75609} &:= \frac{(3 + 1 + 24) \times 8}{7 - 5 + 60 \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31752}{48069} &:= \frac{(3 - 1) \times (7 + 5)^2}{4 + 8 \times 06 \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{32054}{79618} &:= \frac{3 + (2 + 05) \times 4}{7 \times (9 - 6 + 1 \times 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{31406}{85792} &:= \frac{31 + 4 + 06}{8 + 5 + 7 + 92} & \blacktriangleright \frac{31752}{60984} &:= \frac{3 - (1 - 7) \times 52}{609 - 8 + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{32074}{51968} &:= \frac{3 + 2 + 074}{51 + 9 + 68} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{32076}{45198} := \frac{3+20-7+6}{4 \times 5+19-8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32076}{91854} := \frac{3+20-7+6}{9 \times 1 \times (8-5+4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32076}{98415} := \frac{3 \times (2-0+7 \times 6)}{9 \times 8 \times (4+1)+5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32085}{47196} := \frac{(3+20+8) \times 5}{4 \times (7 \times 1 \times 9-6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32154}{76890} := \frac{3 \times (2+1+5 \times 4)}{7+68+90} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32154}{97860} := \frac{3+2 \times (1+5+4)}{9-7+8+60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32186}{97405} := \frac{3+21+8+6}{(9 \times 7-40) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32410}{67598} := \frac{3+2^{4+1}+0}{6 \times (7+5)+9-8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32457}{80619} := \frac{3+2^4+5+7}{80+6-1 \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32480}{91756} := \frac{(3+2) \times 48+0}{9 \times (1+75)-6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32480}{96715} := \frac{(32-4) \times 8+0}{96 \times 7 \times 1-5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32508}{69174} := \frac{(3+2) \times 50+8}{6 \times 91+7-4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32508}{71946} := \frac{(3+2) \times 50+8}{7+1 \times 94 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32508}{74691} := \frac{3 \times (2+5) \times 08}{7 \times (46+9)+1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32508}{91476} := \frac{3-2+50-8}{9 \times (1+4)+76} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32589}{61047} := \frac{3 \times (2 \times 5 \times 8-9)}{(61-04) \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32589}{67014} := \frac{3 \times (2 \times 5 \times 8-9)}{6 \times (70-1+4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32604}{97185} := \frac{(32-6) \times 04}{(9 \times (7-1)+8) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32619}{54780} := \frac{3+2^{6+1^9}}{5 \times 4 \times 7+80} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{32760}{41958} := \frac{(3 \times 2+7) \times 60}{41+958} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32760}{91854} := \frac{(32+7) \times 60}{9^{1^{85} \times 4}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32795}{68401} := \frac{(3+2-7+9) \times 5}{6 \times (8+4)+01} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32805}{41796} := \frac{3+2+80 \times 5}{4+(1+7)^{9-6}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32805}{49167} := \frac{3+2+80 \times 5}{4+9 \times 1 \times 67} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32805}{61479} := \frac{3+2+805}{6 \times (1+4 \times 7 \times 9)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32805}{79461} := \frac{3 \times (2+8+05)}{7 \times 9+46 \times 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32810}{97465} := \frac{32-8+10}{97+4 \times (6-5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32967}{41580} := \frac{3 \times (2 \times (9+6)+7)}{4 \times 15+80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32967}{51084} := \frac{3 \times (2 \times (9+6)+7)}{(51-08) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32967}{51840} := \frac{3+29 \times 6 \times 7}{(5+1) \times 8 \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32976}{84501} := \frac{3+29 \times (7-6)}{8 \times 4+50 \times 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{32981}{70564} := \frac{3+2 \times 9 \times (8-1)}{(70+5-6) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34017}{85629} := \frac{3 \times 4+017}{8+5 \times (6-2+9)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34056}{71928} := \frac{(3+40) \times (5+6)}{71+928} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34056}{71982} := \frac{3 \times 40+56}{(71-9) \times (8-2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34056}{89712} := \frac{(3+40) \times (5+6)}{89 \times 7 \times 1 \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34125}{87906} := \frac{3+4+(1+2)^5}{8+7 \times 90+6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34128}{56970} := \frac{(3^4 \times 1-2) \times 8}{5+(6+9) \times 70} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{34170}{58692} := \frac{3 \times (4+1)+70}{(58+6+9) \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34209}{71568} := \frac{3^4 \times 20+9}{71 \times (56-8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34278}{59160} := \frac{(3+4) \times 27+8}{5 \times (9-1+60)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34278}{91605} := \frac{3 \times 4 \times (2+7)+8}{9+1+60 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34281}{59670} := \frac{3+4 \times 2^{8+1}}{(5 \times 9+6) \times 70} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34290}{76581} := \frac{(3-4+2) \times 90}{7 \times 6 \times 5-8-1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34502}{96871} := \frac{3 \times (4+50-2)}{9 \times 6 \times 8+7-1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34528}{79016} := \frac{3-4+5+2^8}{7 \times (90+1-6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34560}{78912} := \frac{(3+4-5) \times 60}{7+89 \times (1+2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34560}{91728} := \frac{3 \times 4 \times 560}{91 \times 7 \times 28} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34560}{98172} := \frac{(3+45) \times 60}{9+8172} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34572}{61908} := \frac{3-4-5+7^2}{6-1+9 \times 08} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34612}{89075} := \frac{34 \times 6^{1^2}}{(8+90+7) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34692}{71508} := \frac{(3+46) \times (9-2)}{715-08} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34809}{72165} := \frac{3^4-8+09}{7-2+165} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34821}{70956} := \frac{3+48+2 \times 1}{7+095+6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34860}{71295} := \frac{34 \times 8+60}{7 \times 1 \times (2+95)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34907}{68251} := \frac{3+4 \times (9+07)}{68 \times 2-5 \times 1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{34916}{52780} := \frac{(34+9) \times 16}{5 \times 2^7+80} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{34970}{52186} &:= \frac{3^4 - 9 - 7 + 0}{5 \times 2 + 1 + 86} & \blacktriangleright \frac{35612}{74908} &:= \frac{(3 + 56 - 1) \times 2}{7 \times 4 \times 9 - 08} & \blacktriangleright \frac{36019}{42785} &:= \frac{3 \times 60 + 1^9}{4 + 27 \times 8 - 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{35046}{81972} &:= \frac{35 + 04 \times 6}{8 \times (1 + 9 + 7) + 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{35621}{80794} &:= \frac{356 + 2 \times 1}{807 + 9 - 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{36019}{84527} &:= \frac{3 \times 60 + 19}{8 + 452 + 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{35046}{87912} &:= \frac{35 + 04 \times 6}{8 + 7 \times (9 + 1) \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{35640}{71928} &:= \frac{3 + 56 - 4 + 0}{7 \times (19 - 2) - 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{36075}{94128} &:= \frac{360 - 7 \times 5}{(94 + 12) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{35084}{97216} &:= \frac{(350 + 8) \times 4}{(9 \times 7)^2 - 1^6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{35640}{87219} &:= \frac{3 \times 5 \times 6 \times 4 + 0}{872 + 1 \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{36084}{71295} &:= \frac{360 + 8 + 4}{7 \times (12 + 9) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{35092}{87164} &:= \frac{(3 + 5 + 09) \times 2}{8 + 71 - 6 + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{35712}{40896} &:= \frac{3 + (5 + 7 - 1)^2}{40 + (8 + 9) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{36108}{95472} &:= \frac{3 + (6 + 1) \times 08}{(9 + 5) \times (4 + 7) + 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{35096}{74128} &:= \frac{35 \times 09 + 6}{7^4 - 1 \times 2 - 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{35712}{96480} &:= \frac{3 + (5 + 7 - 1)^2}{9 + 6 + 4 \times 80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{36120}{47859} &:= \frac{(3 + 6 + 1) \times 20}{4^{7-8+5} + 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{35109}{68724} &:= \frac{3^5 + 1 - 09}{68 \times 7 - 2^4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{35721}{86940} &:= \frac{35 + 7^{2+1}}{(8 + 6 + 9) \times 40} & \blacktriangleright \frac{36125}{49708} &:= \frac{3^{6-1} + 2 + 5}{(4 \times 9 + 7) + 0 \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{35190}{72864} &:= \frac{3 \times 51 \times 90}{(7 \times 2 + 8) \times 6^4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{35724}{96180} &:= \frac{3 + 5 + 7 + 24}{96 + 1 + 8 + 0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{36180}{95274} &:= \frac{3 \times (6 - 1) \times 8 + 0}{(9 + 5 \times 2 \times 7) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{35192}{48760} &:= \frac{3^{5-1^9} + 2}{48 + 7 + 60} & \blacktriangleright \frac{35802}{64719} &:= \frac{(3 - 5 + 80) \times 2}{6 \times 47^{1^9}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{36192}{47850} &:= \frac{3 \times (61 + 9) - 2}{(47 + 8) \times 5 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{35216}{98704} &:= \frac{(35 \times 2 + 1) \times 6}{(9 + 8) \times 70 + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{35802}{96174} &:= \frac{35 + 8 \times 02}{9 \times (6 + 1) + 74} & \blacktriangleright \frac{36207}{49815} &:= \frac{3 + 6 + 20 \times 7}{(49 - 8 \times 1) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{35219}{80746} &:= \frac{35 - 2 - 1 + 9}{8 \times (07 + 4) + 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{35802}{97614} &:= \frac{35 + 80 + 2}{9 \times 7 \times (6 - 1) + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{36207}{98415} &:= \frac{3 + 6 + 20 \times 7}{9 \times (8 \times (4 + 1) + 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{35280}{41976} &:= \frac{(3^5 + 2) \times 8 + 0}{4 \times (1 + 97 \times 6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{35862}{91740} &:= \frac{3 \times (5 + 8) + 6 - 2}{(9 + 1) \times (7 + 4) + 0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{36208}{41975} &:= \frac{3 \times 62 \times 08}{(4 + 19) \times 75} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{35280}{47916} &:= \frac{35 \times 28 + 0}{(4 + 7)^{9-1 \times 6}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{35910}{46872} &:= \frac{35 \times (9 + 10)}{(4 + 6) \times 87 - 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{36210}{94785} &:= \frac{3 \times (6 + 2) + 10}{9 + 4 \times (7 + 8 + 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{35280}{69174} &:= \frac{35 \times 2 \times 8 + 0}{6 \times (9 + 174)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{35910}{62874} &:= \frac{3 \times 5 \times (9 + 10)}{62 \times 8 + 7 - 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{36218}{49750} &:= \frac{3^6 - 2 + 1^8}{(4 + 9 + 7) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{35280}{97461} &:= \frac{3 - 5 + 2 + 80}{(9 + 7 \times 4) \times 6 - 1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{35910}{67284} &:= \frac{3 \times 5 \times (9 + 10)}{6 \times (7 - 2 + 84)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{36270}{59148} &:= \frac{3 - 6 - 2 + 70}{59 - 1 + 48} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{35416}{97280} &:= \frac{3^5 - 4 - 1 \times 6}{9 \times 72 - 8 + 0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{35910}{68742} &:= \frac{(3^5 + 9) \times 10}{6 + (8 + 7^4) \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{36278}{50149} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 \times (2 + 7 + 8)}{(50 + 1 - 4) \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{35490}{72618} &:= \frac{3 \times 5 \times (4 + 9) + 0}{7 \times (2^6 + 1 - 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{35910}{78624} &:= \frac{3 \times 5 \times (9 + 10)}{78 \times (6 - 2 + 4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{36410}{85729} &:= \frac{(3 \times 6 + 4) \times 10}{8 + 5 - 7 + 2^9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{35496}{87210} &:= \frac{3^5 + 4 - 9 - 6}{(8 + 7^2) \times 10} & \blacktriangleright \frac{35910}{84672} &:= \frac{35 \times (9 + 10)}{(8 + 4 \times 6) \times 7^2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{36450}{79218} &:= \frac{3 \times (6 - 4) \times 50}{7 \times 92 \times 1 + 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{35604}{91287} &:= \frac{3 \times 56 + 04}{9 \times (1 - 2 + 8) \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{35986}{40721} &:= \frac{3^5 + 9 + 8 + 6}{40 \times 7 + 21} & \blacktriangleright \frac{36450}{91728} &:= \frac{(3 + 6) \times 450}{91 \times 7 \times 2 \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{36480}{71592} := \frac{(3-6+4) \times 80}{71+5+9^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{36498}{50127} := \frac{(3+6) \times 4 \times 9-8}{(50+12) \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{36498}{70152} := \frac{3+6+4 \times (9+8)}{(70-1+5) \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{36504}{91728} := \frac{3 \times 65 \times 04}{(9+1) \times 7 \times 28} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{36504}{92781} := \frac{3+65+04}{(9+2 \times 7) \times 8-1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{36540}{72819} := \frac{36 \times 5-40}{7+281-9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{36549}{78120} := \frac{36 \times 5-49}{(7+8-1) \times 20} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{36570}{49128} := \frac{3 \times 65+70}{4 \times (9^{1 \times 2}+8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{36570}{94128} := \frac{(3+6) \times 5+70}{(9 \times 4+1^2) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{36720}{49815} := \frac{36 \times 7+20}{4+(9 \times 8+1) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{36720}{51948} := \frac{3^6-7^2+0}{5 \times 194-8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{36720}{91584} := \frac{36+7^2+0}{(9 \times 1 \times 5+8) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{36720}{91854} := \frac{3^6-7^2+0}{9 \times (185+4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{36720}{98415} := \frac{36 \times 7+20}{9^{8-4-1^5}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{36729}{41580} := \frac{3+6+7 \times 29}{(4-1^5) \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{36729}{48510} := \frac{(3+6+7)^2+9}{4 \times 85+10} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{36751}{82940} := \frac{36 \times 7+5 \times 1}{8^2 \times 9+4+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{36792}{51408} := \frac{3+(6+7) \times (9+2)}{51 \times 4+0 \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{36792}{80154} := \frac{3-67+92}{8-01+54} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{36792}{85410} := \frac{3-67+92}{(8+5) \times (4+1)+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{36801}{59247} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 8-01}{5 \times (9+2) \times 4+7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{36801}{75429} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 8-01}{7 \times 5 \times 4 \times 2+9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{36851}{40279} := \frac{3 \times (6 \times 8-5 \times 1)}{4+02^7+9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{36921}{54870} := \frac{36 \times (9+2)+1}{5 \times (48+70)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{36972}{51480} := \frac{3^{6-9+7}-2}{5 \times (14+8)+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{36975}{41820} := \frac{3+6 \times 97-5}{41 \times 8 \times 2+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{36981}{47250} := \frac{3 \times (6 \times 98-1)}{(47-2) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37051}{62489} := \frac{3+70-5-1}{6 \times 2^4+8+9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37054}{86912} := \frac{3 \times (70-5)-4}{8 \times (6 \times 9 \times 1+2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37056}{91482} := \frac{3+7 \times 5-6}{9 \times (1^4+8)-2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37084}{69215} := \frac{(3+70) \times (8-4)}{(6 \times 9 \times 2+1) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37098}{52164} := \frac{3 \times (70+9)-8}{(52+1) \times 6+4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37098}{64152} := \frac{3 \times (70+9)-8}{6 \times (41+5^2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37098}{65124} := \frac{3 \times (70+9)-8}{6 \times (51+2^4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37128}{50694} := \frac{3+7 \times (1-2+8)}{5 \times (06+9)-4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37148}{69025} := \frac{37 \times 1^4 \times 8}{6 \times 90+2 \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37149}{85260} := \frac{3+71-4-9}{8 \times 5^2-60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37152}{40896} := \frac{3 \times (7+(1+5)^2)}{40+(8+9) \times 6} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \blacktriangleright \frac{37152}{96480} := \frac{3 \times (7+(1+5)^2)}{9+6+4 \times 80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37206}{58194} := \frac{37+2+0 \times 6}{58-1^9+4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37240}{61985} := \frac{(3-7) \times (2-40)}{6+19 \times (8+5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37260}{49815} := \frac{3 \times 72+60}{4+(9 \times 8+1) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37268}{94501} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times (2-6+8)}{9+4 \times (50+1)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37294}{61085} := \frac{3-7+294}{6 \times 10 \times 8-5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37296}{41580} := \frac{37 \times (2 \times 9-6)}{415+80} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37410}{85269} := \frac{3+7 \times 41+0}{85+2^6 \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37518}{62049} := \frac{(3 \times 7+5) \times 18}{(6+20 \times 4) \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37518}{90246} := \frac{3 \times (75-1^8)}{90 \times (2+4)-6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37582}{96140} := \frac{3+(7+5+8) \times 2}{9+61+40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37604}{51982} := \frac{3+7+6 \times 04}{5 \times (1^9+8)+2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37620}{51984} := \frac{37 \times 6-2+0}{(5-1+9 \times 8) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37620}{91485} := \frac{376+20}{9 \times (14 \times 8-5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37620}{95418} := \frac{37 \times 6-2+0}{9 \times (54+1 \times 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37658}{49210} := \frac{3+76 \times (5+8)}{(4 \times 9)^2-1+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37680}{95142} := \frac{(3+7 \times 6) \times 8+0}{951-42} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37692}{51840} := \frac{3 \times (7+6) \times 9-2}{(5-1+8) \times 40} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{37819}{60254} := \frac{37+(8+1) \times 9}{6 \times 02^5-4} \end{array}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{37824}{91605} := \frac{3-7+8^2+4}{(91-60) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38190}{45627} := \frac{38 \times (1+9) + 0}{4 \times 5 + 62 \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38907}{64152} := \frac{3+8 \times (9+07)}{6^4-1^{52}}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{37845}{60291} := \frac{(3+7 \times (8+4)) \times 5}{602+91}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38192}{45760} := \frac{3+8 \times 1 \times 9^2}{4 \times 5 + 760}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38957}{62140} := \frac{3+8+9 \times 5 \times 7}{(6 \times 2+1) \times 40}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{37890}{52416} := \frac{3^7+8-90}{(5+2) \times 416}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38241}{60795} := \frac{38 \times 2^4-1}{60 \times (7+9) + 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38976}{54201} := \frac{3-8+9 \times 7+6}{5+4 \times (20+1)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{37890}{56142} := \frac{3^7+8-90}{5^{6-1}-4-2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38250}{41769} := \frac{(38+2) \times 50}{(4-1)^7+6-9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39015}{42687} := \frac{3 \times (90-1 \times 5)}{4+268+7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{37908}{51246} := \frac{37+9+08}{51-2+4 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38250}{64719} := \frac{3 \times (8+2) \times 50}{6 \times 47 \times 1 \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39015}{64872} := \frac{3 \times (90-1 \times 5)}{6^4-872}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{37908}{61425} := \frac{3+7+90+8}{(6+1^4) \times 25}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38259}{71604} := \frac{3 \times (8^2+5 \times 9)}{7+1+604}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39024}{71568} := \frac{3 \times 902+4}{71 \times 5 \times (6+8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{37908}{65124} := \frac{3-7+90-8}{65 \times 1 \times 2+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38295}{41607} := \frac{3-8+2 \times 95}{(4-1) \times (60+7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39042}{57186} := \frac{3^9-0^4-2}{5 \times 71-8+6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{37914}{86052} := \frac{((3+7) \times 9-1) \times 4}{860-52}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38295}{47610} := \frac{3 \times 8+2 \times 9-5}{4+7 \times 6 \times 1+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39042}{71658} := \frac{3+90 \times 4 \times 2}{7+165 \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{37926}{51084} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times (9+2 \times 6)}{510+84}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38467}{91520} := \frac{3+(8+4) \times 67}{(91+5) \times 20}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39042}{75168} := \frac{3^9-0^4-2}{(75+1) \times 6+8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{37926}{51408} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times (92-6)}{51 \times (40+8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38502}{47196} := \frac{38-5-02}{4 \times (7+1^9)+6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39042}{87156} := \frac{3^9-0^4-2}{8 \times 71-5 \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{37962}{40185} := \frac{37 \times (9-6) \times 2}{(40-1+8) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38502}{61479} := \frac{(3+8 \times 50) \times 2}{6^{1-4+7}-9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39078}{52416} := \frac{390-7 \times 8}{(5+2) \times 4 \times 16}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{37962}{81054} := \frac{3+7-9+6^2}{8 \times 10-5+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38502}{69471} := \frac{38+50 \times 2}{6+9 \times (4 \times 7-1)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39102}{87465} := \frac{39+1-02}{(8+7-4+6) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{38014}{56792} := \frac{3+80^{1^4}}{(5-6+7 \times 9) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38570}{49126} := \frac{3+85+7+0}{4+9 \times (1+2 \times 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39105}{42768} := \frac{39 \times 10+5}{(4-2+7) \times 6 \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{38056}{97412} := \frac{3 \times 80 \times 5+6}{9 \times 7^4-1^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38594}{67120} := \frac{3 \times 85-94}{(6+7+1) \times 20}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39105}{46728} := \frac{39 \times 10+5}{4 \times (6+7 \times 2 \times 8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{38097}{54621} := \frac{(3 \times 80+9) \times 7}{(5 \times (4+6))^2-1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38610}{49725} := \frac{(3+8) \times 6 \times 1+0}{4+9 \times (7 \times 2-5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39105}{46827} := \frac{39 \times 10+5}{468-2+7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{38097}{61254} := \frac{3 \times (80-9 \times 7)}{61+25-4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38710}{64925} := \frac{3 \times 8 \times 7-10}{(6+49-2) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39105}{76824} := \frac{39 \times 10+5}{768+2 \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{38125}{46970} := \frac{((3-8) \times (1-2))^5}{(46+9) \times 70}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38715}{69420} := \frac{3+8+71+5}{6 \times (9+4) \times 2+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39105}{82764} := \frac{39 \times 10+5}{8^2 \times (7+6)+4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{38157}{92046} := \frac{(3+81-5) \times 7}{(9+20) \times 46}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38742}{51069} := \frac{3-8+7+42}{5-1+06 \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39105}{86427} := \frac{39 \times 10+5}{864+2+7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{38160}{52947} := \frac{(3+8+1) \times 60}{52+947}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38794}{52160} := \frac{3 \times (87-9)+4}{5 \times 2^{1 \times 6}+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39150}{64728} := \frac{3 \times (9+1) \times 5+0}{(6-4)^7 \times 2-8}$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39168}{40752} := \frac{(39+1-6) \times 8}{40 \times 7 + 5 - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39168}{45072} := \frac{(39+1-6) \times 8}{45 \times 07 - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39168}{47520} := \frac{3 \times (9 \times 16 - 8)}{475 + 20}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39168}{54720} := \frac{(39+1-6) \times 8}{5 \times (4 + 72) + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39204}{51876} := \frac{3 \times (9 + 20 + 4)}{5 \times (18 + 7) + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39204}{57816} := \frac{392 + 04}{578 + 1 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39204}{61578} := \frac{392 + 04}{6 \times 15 \times 7 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39204}{61875} := \frac{3 \times (920 + 4)}{(6-1) \times 875}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39204}{87516} := \frac{3-9+204}{87 \times 5 + 1 + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39270}{45186} := \frac{3 \times (9 + 2) \times 70}{(451 - 8) \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39270}{68145} := \frac{39 + 2 - 7 + 0}{6 + 8 + 1 \times 45}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39456}{70281} := \frac{39 + 4 - 5 - 6}{70^2 + 8 \times 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39480}{72615} := \frac{(3-9) \times 4 + 80}{7 \times 2 \times (6+1) + 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39501}{82467} := \frac{3 + 9 \times (5 + 01)}{8 \times (2 \times 4 + 6) + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39564}{70812} := \frac{3-9+5 \times 64}{70 \times 8 \times 1 + 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39564}{71820} := \frac{3-9+5 \times 64}{71 \times 8 + 2 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39567}{42108} := \frac{3 + 9 \times (5 + 6) + 7}{4 \times (21 + 08)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39576}{41820} := \frac{(395-7) \times 6}{(4-1) \times 820}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39627}{84150} := \frac{(3 + 9 \times 6 \times 2) \times 7}{(8 \times 4 + 1) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39648}{51072} := \frac{3 + (9 - 6 + 4) \times 8}{5 - 1 + 072}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39652}{41807} := \frac{3 + 96 - 5 - 2}{41 + 8 \times 07}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39672}{58140} := \frac{3 \times (9 - 6) + 7^2}{5 \times (8 + 1) + 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39780}{41652} := \frac{3 + 9 - 7 + 80}{4 \times 16 + 5^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39780}{46215} := \frac{3 + 9 + 7 \times 8 + 0}{4 - (6 - 21) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39780}{46512} := \frac{3 \times (9 + 7 \times 8) + 0}{46 \times 5 \times 1 - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39780}{52416} := \frac{3 + 9 - 7 + 80}{(5 - 2 + 4) \times 16}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39780}{61425} := \frac{3 + 9 + 7 \times 8 + 0}{6 - 1 + 4 \times 25}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39812}{54607} := \frac{(3 + 9 \times 8 - 1) \times 2}{(5 + 4 \times 6) \times 07}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39816}{40527} := \frac{3 \times (9 + 8) - 1 + 6}{40^{5-2} - 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39824}{61570} := \frac{(3 \times 9 - 8) \times 2 \times 4}{61 \times 5 - 70}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39852}{46170} := \frac{3 + 9 \times 8 + 5 + 2}{4 \times 6 + 1 + 70}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39861}{42570} := \frac{(3 + 9) \times 8 + 6 + 1}{4 \times 2 \times 5 + 70}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39864}{70215} := \frac{3 + 9^{8-6} + 4}{70 \times 2 + 15}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{39867}{45210} := \frac{(3 + 9) \times 8 - 6 + 7}{4 \times 5^2 + 10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40158}{63729} := \frac{401 + 5 + 8}{6 + 3 + 72 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40176}{53289} := \frac{4 \times (-01 + 7) \times 6}{5 \times (32 + 8) - 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40176}{83592} := \frac{4 \times 017 - 6}{8 + 3 + 59 \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40236}{58917} := \frac{4 \times (-02 + 3 + 6)}{58 - 9 - 1 - 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40257}{61983} := \frac{4 + 02 + 57}{6 - 1 + 9 + 83}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40271}{53869} := \frac{4 + 02 + 71}{5 + 3 + 86 + 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40356}{97128} := \frac{4 \times (03 + 56)}{9 \times (7 + 1)^2 - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40386}{57912} := \frac{40 + (3 + 8) \times 6}{5 + 7 \times (9 + 12)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40392}{51867} := \frac{4 + 03 + 9^2}{5 \times (18 + 6) - 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40392}{51876} := \frac{40 \times 3 - 9 \times 2}{5 \times (18 + 7) + 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40392}{57618} := \frac{(40 + 3 - 9) \times 2}{57 + (6 - 1) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40392}{65178} := \frac{4 + 03 + 9^2}{65 - 1 + 78}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40528}{76139} := \frac{40 \times (5 + 2) - 8}{7 \times (61 + 3 + 9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40572}{96138} := \frac{4 \times 05 + 72}{(9 + 61) \times 3 + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40658}{79213} := \frac{(4 + 06) \times 5 + 8}{7 \times 9 \times 2 - 13}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40683}{51972} := \frac{406 - 8 \times 3}{5 \times (1 + 97) - 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40689}{75213} := \frac{40 - 6 + 8 - 9}{7 + 52 - 1 + 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40716}{85293} := \frac{4 + 07 \times 16}{(8 - 5)^2 \times 9 \times 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40716}{95823} := \frac{4 + 07 \times 16}{9 \times 5 \times (8 - 2) + 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40836}{51792} := \frac{4 \times 08 + 3 + 6}{5 \times (1^7 + 9) + 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40851}{67932} := \frac{4 + 085 \times 1}{67 + 9 \times 3^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40893}{67521} := \frac{40 - (8 - 9) \times 3}{6^{7-5} \times 2 - 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{40896}{73152} := \frac{40 + (8 + 9) \times 6}{7 \times (31 + 5) + 2}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{41038}{56729} &:= \frac{(4+10) \times 3 - 8}{5+6+7+29} & \blacktriangleright \frac{41856}{73902} &:= \frac{(4+1-8+5)^6}{7 \times 3+90+2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{42639}{58017} &:= \frac{4+2 \times 6^3 - 9}{580+1^7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{41072}{83956} &:= \frac{4 \times (10+7) \times 2}{8 \times (39-5)+6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{41860}{93275} &:= \frac{4 \times 1 \times 8+60}{(9 \times 3+2 \times 7) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{42687}{95013} &:= \frac{(4-2) \times (6+87)}{9 \times (50-1-3)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{41205}{76983} &:= \frac{41 \times 2 \times 05}{7+69 \times (8+3)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{41895}{72063} &:= \frac{(41+8) \times 95}{7+20^{6-3}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{42693}{51870} &:= \frac{(42-6) \times 9-3}{5 \times 1 \times (8+70)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{41265}{83709} &:= \frac{4-1+2+6 \times 5}{8 \times (3+7)-09} & \blacktriangleright \frac{41902}{63875} &:= \frac{(4-1) \times 902}{(63-8) \times 75} & \blacktriangleright \frac{42718}{90365} &:= \frac{(4+2+7) \times 18}{(90+3+6) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{41293}{86750} &:= \frac{4 \times 1 \times 29+3}{(8+6 \times 7) \times 5+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{41923}{58760} &:= \frac{4 \times 1 \times 92+3}{5 \times 8 \times (7+6)+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{42750}{83961} &:= \frac{(4 \times 2+7) \times 50}{8^3+961} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{41325}{87609} &:= \frac{4-1-3+25}{8 \times 7+6-09} & \blacktriangleright \frac{41925}{80367} &:= \frac{(4+1 \times 9) \times 25}{(80+3+6) \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{42768}{50193} &:= \frac{(4-2+7) \times 6 \times 8}{501+9-3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{41328}{57960} &:= \frac{4^{1+3} - 2 - 8}{5 \times (7 \times 9+6)+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{41958}{62370} &:= \frac{4+1+(9-5) \times 8}{6 \times 2^3+7+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{42795}{61830} &:= \frac{4-2+7 \times 9 \times 5}{61 \times 8-30} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{41382}{70965} &:= \frac{4 \times 1 \times (3+8)^2}{(70+96) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{41976}{53280} &:= \frac{4 \times (1+97 \times 6)}{(5+32) \times 80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{42813}{67095} &:= \frac{4+(2+8) \times 13}{6 \times 7 \times (0 \times 9+5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{41538}{62790} &:= \frac{4+15+3 \times 8}{(6+2) \times 7+9+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{42107}{96538} &:= \frac{4 \times (2+10)-7}{9 \times (6+5)+3-8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{42896}{50173} &:= \frac{4 \times 28 \times (9-6)}{50+1 \times 7^3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{41580}{76329} &:= \frac{4 \times 15+80}{7 \times (6+32)-9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{42108}{76593} &:= \frac{4 \times (21+08)}{76+5 \times 9 \times 3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{42908}{76351} &:= \frac{4 \times 2 \times (9+08)}{(7-6) \times (3^5-1)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{41580}{79632} &:= \frac{415+80}{79 \times (6+3 \times 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{42160}{95387} &:= \frac{4 \times (2+1) \times 60}{9 \times (5^3+8 \times 7)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{42957}{86301} &:= \frac{(4+2) \times 9+57}{8+6^3-01} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{41652}{87309} &:= \frac{(4-1) \times 6 \times 52}{(8+7 \times 30) \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{42180}{69375} &:= \frac{4 \times 21-8+0}{(6+9+3+7) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{43056}{81972} &:= \frac{4+(3+05) \times 6}{8+19+72} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{41683}{75920} &:= \frac{41 \times (6+8)-3}{(7+5 \times 9) \times 20} & \blacktriangleright \frac{42180}{79365} &:= \frac{4 \times 21-8+0}{(7+9-3) \times (6+5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{43081}{72659} &:= \frac{4 \times 30+81}{(72-6) \times 5+9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{41736}{58092} &:= \frac{4 \times (17+3)-6}{5+80+9 \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{42315}{87906} &:= \frac{(4-2) \times 31 \times 5}{8+7 \times 90+6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{43089}{56127} &:= \frac{4+3 \times 089}{5 \times 6 \times 12-7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{41796}{58320} &:= \frac{4 \times 1 \times 7 \times 9+6}{5 \times 8 \times 3^2+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{42513}{60897} &:= \frac{4 \times 2 \times 5 \times 1-3}{60+(8-9) \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{43092}{86751} &:= \frac{4 \times (3+092)}{8+6+751} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{41796}{83205} &:= \frac{4+1+7+96}{(8+3) \times 20-5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{42579}{83106} &:= \frac{4+(25-7) \times 9}{8+310+6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{43095}{81627} &:= \frac{(43-09) \times 5}{(8 \times 1 \times 6-2) \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{41832}{60795} &:= \frac{4 \times 1 \times 83 \times 2}{60 \times (7+9)+5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{42581}{90376} &:= \frac{(4^2+5) \times (8-1)}{90+37 \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{43120}{86975} &:= \frac{(43+1)^2+0}{(86 \times 9+7) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{41832}{70965} &:= \frac{4-(1-83) \times 2}{(7 \times 09-6) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{42598}{61370} &:= \frac{4+2+5 \times 9+8}{6 \times 13+7-0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{43152}{90768} &:= \frac{4 \times 3+15+2}{9 \times 07+6-8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{41839}{50267} &:= \frac{4+(18-3) \times 9}{50 \times 2+67} & \blacktriangleright \frac{42630}{89175} &:= \frac{4+2^6 \times 3+0}{(89-1 \times 7) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{43250}{71968} &:= \frac{(4+3 \times 2) \times 50}{(7+1+96) \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{43281}{60795} := \frac{43 \times 2 \times 8 - 1}{60 \times (7+9) + 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45287}{93610} := \frac{4 + 5 \times (28 + 7)}{9 + 361 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46035}{71982} := \frac{4 \times 60 + 35}{(7-1) \times 9 \times 8 - 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{43290}{75816} := \frac{43 + 2^9 + 0}{(7-5) \times 81 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45312}{86907} := \frac{4^{5-3+1 \times 2}}{8 + 69 \times 07}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46053}{71982} := \frac{4 \times 60 - 5 + 3}{(71-9) \times (8-2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{43290}{85176} := \frac{43 + 2^9 + 0}{(85-1) \times (7+6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45360}{81792} := \frac{(45-3) \times 60}{8 \times (1+7 \times 9^2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46137}{89250} := \frac{4+6+1 \times 3^7}{(8+9) \times 250}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{43512}{97608} := \frac{4-3+(5+1)^2}{97-6-08}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45360}{87129} := \frac{4 \times 5 \times 36 + 0}{871 + 2^9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46197}{82305} := \frac{4 \times 6 \times 1 + 9 \times 7}{(8+23) \times 05}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{43512}{97680} := \frac{(4 \times (3+5-1))^2}{(9+7+6) \times 80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45360}{91287} := \frac{4 \times 5 \times 36 + 0}{91 \times 2 \times 8 - 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46230}{71958} := \frac{46 \times (2+3) + 0}{7 \times (1+9) \times 5 + 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{43516}{92708} := \frac{4 + 35 - 16}{9 - (2-7) \times 08}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45360}{98721} := \frac{4 \times 5 \times 36 + 0}{9 \times 87 \times 2 + 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46275}{98103} := \frac{4-6+2+75}{9 \times (8+10) - 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{43560}{87912} := \frac{435 + 60}{87 + 912}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45368}{70192} := \frac{4 + 5 + 36 + 8}{70 + 1 + 9 + 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46305}{91287} := \frac{(4 \times 6 - 3) \times 05}{9 \times 1 \times (2 \times 8 + 7)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{43560}{91872} := \frac{43 \times 5 + 60}{(9+1) \times (8 \times 7 + 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45621}{93708} := \frac{4 \times (5+6-2) + 1}{(9+3) \times 7 - 08}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46315}{87920} := \frac{4^{6-3 \times 1} - 5}{8 \times (7+9-2) + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{43581}{60297} := \frac{4 \times (3-5) + 81}{6 - 02 + 97}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45627}{81039} := \frac{4 + (5+6-2) \times 7}{8 \times 10 + 39}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46325}{87091} := \frac{4-6+32-5}{8 \times 7 - 09 \times 1}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{43675}{82109} := \frac{(4+3+6+7) \times 5}{8+2 \times 10 \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45630}{72891} := \frac{(4 \times 5 + 6) \times 30}{7 \times 2 \times 89 \times 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46398}{50172} := \frac{4-6 \times (3-9 \times 8)}{501 - 7^2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{43710}{69285} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 7 + 10}{6 + (9+2) \times (8+5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45738}{60192} := \frac{457 - 3 + 8}{601 + 9 - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46398}{72150} := \frac{4-6 \times (3-9 \times 8)}{(7 \times 2 - 1) \times 50}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{43719}{65208} := \frac{4^3 + (7-1) \times 9}{(6+5) \times 2 \times 08}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45738}{92610} := \frac{4 + (57+3) \times 8}{(92+6) \times 10}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46512}{83790} := \frac{4 \times (6 \times (5+1) - 2)}{8 + 3 \times 79 + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{43769}{51208} := \frac{437 + 69}{5 \times 120 - 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45902}{87136} := \frac{4 + 5 \times (9+02)}{8 \times (7+13-6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4653}{102789} := \frac{4 \times 6 - 5 + 3}{(-1 \times 02 + 7 \times 8) \times 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{43802}{57196} := \frac{4 + 3 \times 80 - 2}{5 \times (71-9) + 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45907}{82316} := \frac{4 + 5^{9-07}}{8^2 - (3-1) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46719}{83520} := \frac{46 + 7 \times 19}{(8+3+5) \times 20}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{43928}{70516} := \frac{4 \times (3-9 \times (2-8))}{70 \times 5 + 16}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45927}{83160} := \frac{45 + 927}{(8+3) \times 160}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46728}{50193} := \frac{4 \times (6+7 \times 2 \times 8)}{501 + 9 - 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{45018}{69372} := \frac{4 + 50 - 1 + 8}{6 + 9 \times (3+7) - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45936}{71280} := \frac{4 + 5 \times (9+3) - 6}{7 + 1 + 2 + 80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46782}{90513} := \frac{4 + (6+7+8) \times 2}{90 - 5 + 1 + 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{45103}{69782} := \frac{4 \times (5 \times 10 + 3)}{(6-9+7) \times 82}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45961}{80237} := \frac{4 \times 5 \times (9-6) - 1}{80 + 2 + 3 \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46795}{82130} := \frac{4 - (6-7) \times 9 \times 5}{82 + 1 + 3 + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{45126}{87309} := \frac{4 - (5-12) \times 6}{8 \times (7+3) + 09}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46029}{81753} := \frac{4 \times 6 + 02^9}{8 \times (1-7+5^3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46827}{50193} := \frac{468 - 2 + 7}{501 + 9 - 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{45279}{86301} := \frac{(4-5+2 \times 7) \times 9}{8 + 6^3 - 01}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46031}{92785} := \frac{(4+60) \times 3 - 1}{(92-7-8) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46920}{73185} := \frac{4 \times 69 \times 2 + 0}{7 \times 3 \times (1+8 \times 5)}$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{46970}{81235} := \frac{(4-6) \times (9-70)}{8 \times (1+2)^3 - 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47025}{83619} := \frac{(4+7) \times 025}{83 \times 6 \times 1 - 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47031}{86925} := \frac{4^{7-03} + 1}{(8+6+9^2) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47128}{50396} := \frac{4 \times 71 - 2 - 8}{5 + 03 \times 96}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47152}{96830} := \frac{4 \times 7 \times (1+5) \times 2}{(9+6+8) \times 30}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47163}{82950} := \frac{4 \times 7 \times (1+6) + 3}{(8 \times 2 - 9) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47208}{61539} := \frac{4 \times 7 \times (20-8)}{6 \times (1 + (5+3) \times 9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47215}{69083} := \frac{(47 \times 2 + 1) \times 5}{690 + 8 - 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47310}{86925} := \frac{4 \times (73+10)}{(8 \times (6+9) + 2) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47318}{60952} := \frac{4 + 73 - 18}{60 - 9 + 5^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47329}{51680} := \frac{(47+3)^2 - 9}{(5-1) \times 680}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47601}{85239} := \frac{4 \times (7 \times 6 + 01)}{8 + 5^2 \times (3+9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47610}{59823} := \frac{(4+7 \times 6) \times 10}{5 + 9 \times 8^2 - 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47610}{82593} := \frac{(4+7 \times 6) \times 10}{825 - 9 \times 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47680}{93125} := \frac{4 \times 76 + 80}{(9-3) \times 125}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{47859}{63210} := \frac{47 - 8 + 5 + 9}{(6+3-2) \times 10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48015}{76923} := \frac{480 + 1 \times 5}{7 \times (6 \times 9 \times 2 + 3)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48192}{76053} := \frac{4 \times (8-1+9) \times 2}{7 + (60+5) \times 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48195}{62730} := \frac{4 \times 8 - 1 + 95}{6 + 2^7 + 30}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48195}{67320} := \frac{4 \times 8 \times (1+9) - 5}{6 \times 73 + 2 + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48312}{79605} := \frac{4 \times (8+3 \times 12)}{(7-9+60) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48312}{96075} := \frac{4 \times (8^{3-1} + 2)}{(9+6) \times 07 \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48320}{67195} := \frac{4^{8 \times 3 - 20}}{6 + 7 \times (1+9) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48321}{50976} := \frac{(48-3) \times 2 + 1}{5 + 097 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48321}{79650} := \frac{(4+8)^3 + 2 - 1}{(7 \times 9 - 6) \times 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48503}{79261} := \frac{4 + 8 \times 5 - 03}{79 - 2 \times 6 \times 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48510}{76923} := \frac{(4+8-5) \times 10}{(7 + (6+9) \times 2) \times 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48510}{96327} := \frac{4 \times 85 + 10}{9 \times 63 + 2^7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48723}{96105} := \frac{4 \times 8 \times 7 - 2 \times 3}{(96 - 10) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48756}{93210} := \frac{487 - 5 - 6}{(93 - 2) \times 10}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48762}{90153} := \frac{4 + 8^{7-6+2}}{901 + 53}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{48951}{67032} := \frac{4 \times (89 \times 5 - 1)}{(6+70) \times 32}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49032}{75168} := \frac{4 + 90 \times (3+2)}{(7+5 \times 16) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49068}{71253} := \frac{4 \times (90+6) - 8}{7 \times (1+25) \times 3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49086}{52731} := \frac{490 - 86}{(5+2+7) \times 31}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49203}{56871} := \frac{(-4+9^2) \times 03}{(5 \times 6 + 8) \times 7 + 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49215}{70638} := \frac{4 \times (9^2 - 1 + 5)}{(70 - 6 - 3) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49275}{61830} := \frac{(4-9) \times (2-75)}{61 \times 8 - 30}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49280}{57316} := \frac{4 \times (9+2) \times 80}{5 - 7 + (3+1)^6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49302}{71658} := \frac{4 + 9 + 30^2}{7 + 165 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49305}{76812} := \frac{(49-30) \times 5}{(7+68-1) \times 2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49530}{71628} := \frac{4 \times (95-30)}{(7 \times (1+6) - 2) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49632}{81075} := \frac{4 \times 96 - 32}{(8+107) \times 5}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49651}{70238} := \frac{(4+9) \times 6 + 5 - 1}{70 \times 2 - 3 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49712}{83650} := \frac{(4+9) \times 712}{(8-3)^6 - 50}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49731}{52608} := \frac{4 \times (9+7 \times 3) + 1}{(5 \times 2 + 6) \times 08}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{49815}{76302} := \frac{(49-8) \times 15}{7 \times 6 + 30^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50172}{96348} := \frac{50 + 17^2}{9 - 6 + 3^4 \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50184}{67932} := \frac{50 + 1 \times 8 \times 4}{6 + 7 \times (9+3 \times 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50193}{62478} := \frac{50 + 1 \times 93}{6 \times (24+7) - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50193}{76824} := \frac{501 + 9 - 3}{768 + 2 \times 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50193}{78624} := \frac{50 + 1 \times 93}{7 \times 8 \times (6+2-4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50193}{82764} := \frac{501 + 9 - 3}{8^2 \times (7+6) + 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50193}{86427} := \frac{501 + 9 - 3}{864 + 2 + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50196}{84372} := \frac{50 - 1 \times 9 + 6}{8 - 4 + 3 + 72}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50394}{72186} := \frac{50 - (3-9) \times 4}{7 \times 2 \times 1 \times 8 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50421}{63798} := \frac{50 - 4 + 2 + 1}{6 + 3 \times (7+9) + 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50481}{79632} := \frac{(5+04) \times 8 - 1}{7 \times (9+6+3-2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50692}{81374} := \frac{5-0+69+2}{81+37+4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50732}{84169} := \frac{5+07+32}{8-4+1 \times 69}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50764}{91238} := \frac{(50-7-6) \times 4}{(9-1 \times 2) \times 38}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50784}{91632} := \frac{50+(7-8) \times 4}{9 \times 1 \times (6+3)+2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{50862}{97314} := \frac{(50+8) \times 6 - 2}{9 \times (73+1) - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{51084}{76329} := \frac{(51-08) \times 4}{7 \times (6+32) - 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{51243}{87609} := \frac{5-1+24+3}{8 \times 7+6-09}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{51268}{97043} := \frac{5+1+2+6 \times 8}{9 \times 7+043}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{51642}{83790} := \frac{51+(6+4)^2}{8+3 \times 79+0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{51680}{97432} := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 68+0}{9 \times (7+4^3)+2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{51840}{73926} := \frac{(5+1) \times 8 \times 40}{7 \times 392 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{51840}{79632} := \frac{5 \times 18 \times 4+0}{7 \times (9 \times (6+3) - 2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{51840}{92736} := \frac{5+1+84+0}{9+2 \times 73+6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{51948}{70362} := \frac{5 \times 194 - 8}{7+036^2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{51972}{63048} := \frac{(5-(1-9) \times 7) \times 2}{6 \times (30-4) - 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52038}{67914} := \frac{520+3+8}{679+14}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52041}{68973} := \frac{5+204 \times 1}{6-8 \times 9+7^3}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52073}{89614} := \frac{(5+20) \times 7 - 3}{8 \times (9+(6+1) \times 4)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52104}{93687} := \frac{52 \times (10+4)}{93 \times (6+8) + 7}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52143}{87096} := \frac{5+2 \times 1 \times 43}{8 \times 7+096}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52164}{79380} := \frac{(5+2+16) \times 4}{7 \times (9+3+8) + 0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52316}{87904} := \frac{5-2+316}{8 \times (7 \times 9+04)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52380}{74196} := \frac{5+2 \times 3 \times 80}{741-9 \times 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52394}{70618} := \frac{5+2+3+9+4}{7+06+18}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52416}{79380} := \frac{(5 \times 2)^4 - 16}{7 \times 9 \times 3 \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52438}{61790} := \frac{5+(2^4+3) \times 8}{6+179+0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52470}{63918} := \frac{52-4+7+0}{6-3+(9-1) \times 8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52481}{69730} := \frac{52 \times (4 \times 8+1)}{(69+7) \times 30}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52716}{93840} := \frac{5^2 \times 7+16}{(93-8) \times 4+0}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52731}{86940} := \frac{527+31}{(8+6+9) \times 40}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52734}{81906} := \frac{5^2+73-4}{8 \times 19-06}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52780}{91364} := \frac{5 \times (2+7 \times 8) + 0}{(9-1)^3 - 6 - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52836}{97104} := \frac{5+2^{8+3-6}}{(9+7+1) \times 04}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{52910}{78364} := \frac{5+2 \times 9 \times 10}{(7+8) \times 3 \times 6+4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53064}{91872} := \frac{5 \times (3+064)}{(9+1) \times (8 \times 7+2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53124}{97860} := \frac{5+31-2+4}{9-7+8+60}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53148}{70692} := \frac{5^3 - 14 - 8}{70+69-2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53240}{79618} := \frac{(53+2) \times 4+0}{7 \times (9 \times 6+1-8)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53298}{70641} := \frac{5^3+2-9+8}{7 \times 06 \times 4-1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53417}{62809} := \frac{(5+3+4+1) \times 7}{6^2+80-9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53460}{79218} := \frac{5^3 \times 4 - 60}{7 \times 92 \times 1+8}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53460}{87219} := \frac{534+6+0}{872+1 \times 9}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53460}{98172} := \frac{5 \times (3-4) + 60}{98+1^7+2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53482}{76109} := \frac{(53+4+8) \times 2}{76+109}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53714}{90862} := \frac{53 \times (7+1) + 4}{90 \times 8+6-2}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53790}{82641} := \frac{5 \times (3+7 \times 9) + 0}{8 \times 2^6 - 4 - 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53802}{97461} := \frac{5 \times 3 \times 8 + 02}{(9+7 \times 4) \times 6 - 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{53901}{64872} := \frac{5 \times (3+901)}{64 \times (87-2)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54027}{68931} := \frac{5 \times 4 + 02 + 7}{6^{8-9+3} + 1}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54201}{93786} := \frac{5+4 \times (20+1)}{(9 \times 3 - 7) \times 8 - 6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54219}{60738} := \frac{5-42 \times (1-9)}{60 \times 7-38}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54270}{68139} := \frac{5 \times 4 \times 27+0}{6 \times (8 \times 13+9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54302}{87169} := \frac{54+30 \times 2}{8+7 \times (16+9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54362}{91780} := \frac{(5^4 - 3 - 6) \times 2}{(9+17) \times 80}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54372}{98106} := \frac{5 \times 4 \times 3 - 7 \times 2}{9+8 \times 10-6}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{54720}{81396} := \frac{5 \times (4 \times 7+20)}{(8+1) \times 39+6}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{54720}{83619} := \frac{(5+4+7) \times 20}{83 \times 6 \times 1 - 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{57120}{86394} := \frac{5 \times (7+1) \times 2 + 0}{86 + 39 - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{58491}{72360} := \frac{5 + 84 + 9 - 1}{(7 - 2 - 3) \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{54780}{91632} := \frac{54 - 7 + 8 + 0}{9 \times (1 + 6 + 3) + 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{57168}{90432} := \frac{5 + 7 \times (1 + 6) \times 8}{90 \times (4 + 3) - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{58920}{74136} := \frac{5 + 8 \times 920}{(7 \times (4 - 1))^3 + 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{54891}{67203} := \frac{(5 \times 4 - 8) \times 9 - 1}{6 + (7 - 2)^{03}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{57216}{98304} := \frac{5 + (7 + 2) \times 16}{(9 - 8 + 3)^{04}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{59143}{82076} := \frac{(5 + 9) \times 14 \times 3}{(8 + 2^{07}) \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{54913}{72806} := \frac{5 - 4 + 91 - 3}{7 \times 2 \times 8 + 06}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{57280}{61934} := \frac{5 \times (72 - 8) + 0}{6 \times 19 \times 3 + 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{59160}{72384} := \frac{5 \times (9 - 1 + 60)}{(7 + 2 \times 3) \times 8 \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{54918}{62037} := \frac{5 \times 4 \times (9 + 18)}{620 - 3 - 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{57420}{86391} := \frac{5 \times (7 + 4) \times 20}{8 \times (6^3 - 9) - 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{59182}{60347} := \frac{(5 + 9) \times 18 + 2}{(60 + 3) \times 4 + 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{54931}{87620} := \frac{(5 + 49) \times 3 + 1}{8 + 7 \times 6^2 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{57420}{86913} := \frac{(5 + 7 \times 4) \times 20}{86 + 913}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{59184}{63072} := \frac{5 + 9 + 1 \times 8^4}{6 + 3^{07} \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{54963}{78120} := \frac{5 + 4^{9-6} \times 3}{(7 + 8 - 1) \times 20}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{57420}{98136} := \frac{57 - 4 + 2 + 0}{98 - 1 + 3 - 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{59280}{73164} := \frac{5 \times 92 - 80}{7 \times (3 + 1 \times 64)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{56018}{73429} := \frac{5 + 60 + 1 + 8}{7 + (3 \times 4 - 2) \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{57694}{82103} := \frac{5 \times (7 + 6 + 9 + 4)}{82 + 103}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{59280}{73416} := \frac{5 \times (9 \times 2 + 8) + 0}{7 \times (3 + 4 + 16)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{56173}{82940} := \frac{5 + 6 \times (1 + 7) \times 3}{(8^2 - 9) \times 4 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{57834}{92610} := \frac{578 + 34}{(92 + 6) \times 10}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{59340}{86172} := \frac{5 \times (9 - 3 + 40)}{8 \times 6 \times 1 \times 7 - 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{56238}{79104} := \frac{(56 + 2) \times 3 + 8}{(7 \times 9 + 1) \times 04}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{57902}{61438} := \frac{5 + 7 \times 9 \times 02}{6 + (1 + 4)^3 + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{59360}{84217} := \frac{(5 \times 9 + 3) \times 60}{8^4 - 2 - 1 - 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{56304}{81972} := \frac{5 + 63 + 0 \times 4}{8 + 19 + 72}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{57904}{81263} := \frac{(5 - 7 + 90) \times 4}{8^{1+2} - 6 \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{59670}{82134} := \frac{5 \times (9 - 6) + 70}{82 + 1 + 34}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{56304}{91287} := \frac{(5 + 63) \times 04}{9 \times (1 - 2 + 8) \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{57942}{86130} := \frac{5 + 7 + 9 + 4^2}{86 - 1 - 30}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{59724}{86031} := \frac{(5 + 9 + 7) \times 2^4}{8 \times 60 + 3 + 1}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{56329}{71804} := \frac{5^{6-3} + 2^9}{7 + 1 + 804}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{58160}{79243} := \frac{5 \times 8 \times 1 \times 6 + 0}{(79 + 2) \times 4 + 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{59840}{73216} := \frac{5 \times (98 + 4) + 0}{(7 + 32) \times 16}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{56342}{80179} := \frac{5 \times (6 + 3) \times 4 + 2}{80 + 179}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{58176}{90432} := \frac{5 \times 81 - 7 + 6}{90 \times (4 + 3) - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{60192}{83754} := \frac{601 + 9 - 2}{837 + 5 + 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{56832}{79104} := \frac{5 + 68 + 3 - 2}{7 \times 9 + 10 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{58194}{76320} := \frac{58 - 1^9 + 4}{(7 - 6 + 3) \times 20}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{60273}{84915} := \frac{60 \times (2 + 7) + 3}{8 \times (4 + 91) + 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{56940}{71832} := \frac{5 + (6 + 9) \times 4 + 0}{7 \times (1 + 8 + 3) - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{58240}{91637} := \frac{5 \times 8 \times 2^4 + 0}{(9 + 1^6)^3 + 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{60291}{73458} := \frac{6 \times 029 \times 1}{(7 - 3) \times (45 + 8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{56943}{87210} := \frac{56 - 9 + 4^3}{(8 + 7 + 2) \times 10}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{58293}{61047} := \frac{(5 \times 8 + 2) \times 9 + 3}{(61 - 04) \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{60291}{74385} := \frac{60 + 2 \times 9 - 1}{((7 - 4)^3 - 8) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{57024}{83916} := \frac{5 \times 70 - 2 + 4}{(83 - 9) \times (1 + 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{58293}{67014} := \frac{(5 \times 8 + 2) \times 9 + 3}{6 \times (70 - 1 + 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{60291}{85347} := \frac{60 + 2 \times 9 - 1}{8 \times 5 \times 3 - 4 - 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{57043}{92168} := \frac{5 + (70 - 4) \times 3}{(9 + 2 \times 16) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{58320}{96714} := \frac{5 \times 8 \times 3^2 + 0}{9 + 6 \times 7 \times 14}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{60358}{71492} := \frac{60 + 3 + 5 \times 8}{71 + 49 + 2}$

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{60372}{89154} := \frac{(6+037) \times 2}{8 \times 9 + 1 + 54} & \blacktriangleright \frac{61830}{92475} := \frac{61 \times 8 - 30}{(9 \times 2^4 - 7) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{63270}{91485} := \frac{(6+3)^2 - 7 + 0}{(9+1+4) \times 8 - 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{60398}{74152} := \frac{6 \times (03+98)}{741+5-2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{61950}{78234} := \frac{(6+1^9) \times 50}{(7+8-2) \times 34} & \blacktriangleright \frac{63428}{70195} := \frac{634+2-8}{70 \times (1+9) - 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{60528}{73914} := \frac{(6+05+2) \times 8}{7+3 \times (9+1) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{62034}{91785} := \frac{6 \times (20-3) - 4}{(9+1) \times (7+8) - 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{63495}{70218} := \frac{6+34+9 \times 5}{70+(2+1) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{60528}{91374} := \frac{(6+05+2) \times 8}{9+1 \times 37 \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{62307}{94185} := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 3 + 07}{9+4 \times (1+8+5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{63504}{71928} := \frac{6^3 - 5 \times 04}{(7-1) \times (9+28)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{60532}{71984} := \frac{60+53-2}{(7+1+9) \times 8 - 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{62370}{91854} := \frac{6 \times 2^3 + 7 - 0}{9 \times (1+8 \times (5-4))} & \blacktriangleright \frac{63510}{84972} := \frac{(63-5) \times 10}{(8-4) \times 97 \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{60573}{82419} := \frac{60+5-7+3}{8 \times 2 \times 4 + 19} & \blacktriangleright \frac{62370}{98415} := \frac{(6^2-3) \times 70}{9^{8-4-1} \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{63759}{84210} := \frac{6 \times (3+7 \times 5 \times 9)}{(8+4) \times 210} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{60738}{91425} := \frac{60 \times 7 - 38}{(9+14) \times 25} & \blacktriangleright \frac{62403}{97185} := \frac{62-4+03}{97+1-8+5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{63825}{97014} := \frac{6 \times (3+82) \times 5}{(970-1) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{60792}{81354} := \frac{6 \times 079 + 2}{8+1+3+5^4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{62415}{83790} := \frac{62-4+15}{8+(3+7) \times 9+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{63840}{71592} := \frac{6 \times 3 \times 8 - 4 + 0}{71+5+9^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{60931}{72485} := \frac{6 \times 093 + 1}{(7-2)^4 + 8 \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{62478}{93015} := \frac{6 \times (24+7) - 8}{9 \times 30 \times 1 - 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{63910}{74285} := \frac{63+91+0}{(7+4^2) \times 8 - 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{61047}{89352} := \frac{(61-04) \times 7}{8 \times (9+(3+5)^2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{62481}{70953} := \frac{6+2^4 \times (8-1)}{70+(9-5)^3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{63918}{72504} := \frac{6-3+(9-1) \times 8}{(7 \times 2+5) \times 04} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{61047}{98532} := \frac{(6+10) \times 4 - 7}{9 \times (8+5-3) + 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{62510}{97384} := \frac{6^2 \times 5 + 10}{(9+73-8) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{64125}{83790} := \frac{6+4^{1+2} + 5}{8+(3+7) \times 9+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{61053}{94827} := \frac{6+10+5^3}{9+(4 \times 8-2) \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{62514}{78039} := \frac{(6 \times 25+1) \times 4}{7+(80+3) \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{64251}{90387} := \frac{6+4-2+51}{9 \times 03+8 \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{61054}{87932} := \frac{61+05^4}{8 \times 7 + 932} & \blacktriangleright \frac{62730}{84915} := \frac{6+2+730}{84+915} & \blacktriangleright \frac{64253}{70819} := \frac{6+4+2+5^3}{70+(8+1) \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{61254}{90387} := \frac{61+25-4}{90+38-7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{62730}{98154} := \frac{62-7+30}{9+8 \times 15+4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{64350}{81972} := \frac{(6+4+3) \times 50}{819+7+2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{61408}{75392} := \frac{6+1408}{7 \times (5+3 \times 9^2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{62790}{81354} := \frac{6^2+79+0}{8+1+35 \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{64350}{87219} := \frac{(6+4+3) \times 50}{872+1 \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{61425}{79380} := \frac{(6+1+4+2) \times 5}{79-3+8+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{62810}{75943} := \frac{(6+2 \times 8) \times 10}{7 \times (5+9 \times 4-3)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{64350}{97812} := \frac{6+4^3+5+0}{(9+7) \times (8-1)+2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{61570}{89342} := \frac{61 \times 5 - 70}{8-9+342} & \blacktriangleright \frac{63180}{74529} := \frac{(6-3) \times 180}{7 \times (4 \times 5^2 - 9)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{64701}{95823} := \frac{6+4+70-1}{9 \times (5-8 \times (2-3))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{61803}{72594} := \frac{6 \times (18+03)}{7^2+5+94} & \blacktriangleright \frac{63180}{95472} := \frac{6+31+8+0}{9+54+7-2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{64728}{91350} := \frac{(6-4)^7 \times 2 - 8}{(9+1-3) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{61830}{79245} := \frac{61 \times 8 - 30}{7 \times 9^2 + 4 \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{63270}{84915} := \frac{6+(3-2) \times 70}{(8+4) \times 9 - 1 - 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{64970}{83215} := \frac{6 \times 4 \times 9 - 70}{8 \times (3+21) - 5} \end{array}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{65032}{87941} := \frac{6 \times 5 \times 03 - 2}{87 - 9 + 41}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{65930}{71482} := \frac{6 + 59 + 30}{7 + 1 \times 48 \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{68352}{79104} := \frac{6 + 8 + 3 \times 5^2}{7 \times 9 + 10 \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{65043}{81972} := \frac{650 + 4 + 3}{819 + 7 + 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{67032}{94815} := \frac{6 + (70 + 3) \times 2}{(9 \times 4 + 8 - 1) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{68571}{92340} := \frac{6 + 8 + 5^{7-1}}{9 \times 2340}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{65043}{87219} := \frac{650 + 4 + 3}{872 + 1 \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{67032}{98154} := \frac{6 \times 7 \times 03 \times 2}{9 \times (8 + 1) \times 5 - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{68730}{91245} := \frac{68 - 7 - 3 + 0}{9 \times 1 \times 2 \times 4 + 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{65120}{97384} := \frac{(6 + 5 \times 1) \times 20}{9 + (7 + 3) \times 8 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{67125}{84309} := \frac{(6 \times (7 + 1) + 2) \times 5}{8 + (4 + 30) \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{68742}{91053} := \frac{6 \times (8 + 7 + 42)}{9 \times 10 \times 5 + 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{65124}{78390} := \frac{6 \times (5 - 1 \times 2)^4}{(7 + 8) \times 39 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{67230}{98415} := \frac{(6 + 7)^2 - 3 + 0}{9 \times (8 + 4 + 15)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{68904}{71253} := \frac{(6 - 8 + 90) \times 4}{7 \times (1 - 2 + 53)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{65142}{90783} := \frac{6 \times (5 - 1) \times 4 - 2}{(9 + 07) \times 8 + 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{67284}{90153} := \frac{(6 \times 7 + 2) \times 8 + 4}{9 \times 01 \times 53}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{68931}{74520} := \frac{6 + (8 + 9) \times (3 + 1)}{7 \times 4 + 52 + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{65148}{79032} := \frac{6 + 5 \times (-1 + 4 + 8)}{79 - 03 - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{67405}{81923} := \frac{(6 - 7 + 40) \times 5}{((8 + 1) \times 9 - 2) \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{69015}{78432} := \frac{6 \times 90 \times 1 - 5}{(7 + 8 + 4) \times 32}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{65184}{73920} := \frac{65 + 1 \times 8 \times 4}{(7 + 3) \times (9 + 2) + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{67425}{98310} := \frac{(6 + 74) \times 2 - 5}{9 \times 8 \times 3 + 10}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{69048}{75213} := \frac{(6 + 9 \times 04) \times 8}{7 \times 52 - 1 + 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{65340}{81972} := \frac{6 + 53 - 4 + 0}{8 + 1 \times 9 \times 7 - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{67430}{81529} := \frac{6 + 74 + 30}{(8 - 1) \times (5 \times 2 + 9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{69054}{83271} := \frac{6 \times 9 - 05 \times 4}{8 \times 3 \times 2 - 7 \times 1}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{65340}{87912} := \frac{6 + 53 - 4 + 0}{8 + 7 \times 9 + 1 + 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{67482}{93150} := \frac{6 \times (7 + 482)}{9 \times 3 \times 150}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{69125}{83740} := \frac{(69 + 1) \times 2 \times 5}{8 + 3 \times 7 \times 40}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{65349}{70281} := \frac{6 - 5 + 3 + 49}{70^2 + 8 \times 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{67854}{93102} := \frac{6 + (7 + 8 + 5) \times 4}{(9 + 3) \times 10 - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{69215}{74803} := \frac{(6 \times 9 \times 2 + 1) \times 5}{74 \times 8 - 03}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{65382}{71094} := \frac{65 + (3 \times 8)^2}{710 - 9 - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{67932}{84150} := \frac{6 \times (79 - 3 - 2)}{(8 + 4 - 1) \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{69240}{81357} := \frac{(6 + 9) \times 2 \times 4 + 0}{81 + 3 + 57}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{65403}{91728} := \frac{65 \times (40 + 3)}{(9 + 1) \times 7^2 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{68052}{79341} := \frac{(6 + 80) \times 5 - 2}{7 + (9 + 3) \times 41}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{69258}{73041} := \frac{6 \times (9 + 2^5) - 8}{7 \times 30 + 41}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{65403}{92781} := \frac{65 + 4^{03}}{(9 + 2 \times 7) \times 8 - 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{68125}{93740} := \frac{(6 \times 8 \times 1 + 2) \times 5}{(93 - 7) \times 4 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{69312}{75840} := \frac{(6 + 9 + 3 + 1)^2}{75 + 8 \times 40}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{65412}{70389} := \frac{6 \times 5 \times (4 - 1) + 2}{7 + 03 + 89}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{68145}{72039} := \frac{6 + 8 + 1 + 4 \times 5}{7^2 - 03 - 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{69324}{81750} := \frac{6 + (9 \times 3 - 2) \times 4}{(8 + 17) \times 5 + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{65412}{78039} := \frac{6 + 5^4 + 1^2}{7 + (80 + 3) \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{68210}{73954} := \frac{6 \times 8 \times 2 - 1 + 0}{7 - 3 + 95 + 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{6935}{102784} := \frac{(6 \times 9 + 3) \times 5}{1 \times 02^7 + 8^4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{65709}{83142} := \frac{65 - 7 - 09}{8^3 - 1^4 - 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{68241}{90735} := \frac{6 \times 824 + 1}{90 \times 73 + 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{69471}{80352} := \frac{6 \times 9 + 4 \times 7 + 1}{80 + (3 + 5) \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{65714}{89320} := \frac{6 \times 5 \times 7 \times 1 - 4}{(8 + 9 - 3) \times 20}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{68241}{95703} := \frac{6 \times 824 + 1}{95 \times (70 + 3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{69471}{82305} := \frac{6 + 9 \times (4 \times 7 - 1)}{(8 + 2) \times 30 - 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{65824}{93170} := \frac{65 \times 8 + 24}{(9 + 3 - 1) \times 70}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{68250}{94731} := \frac{(6 \times 8 + 2) \times 5 + 0}{9 - 4 + 7^3 - 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{69720}{83415} := \frac{6^{9-7} + 20}{8 \times 3 \times (4 - 1) - 5}$

$$\begin{array}{lll} \blacktriangleright \frac{70195}{83426} := \frac{70 \times (1+9) - 5}{834 - 2 - 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{72459}{80316} := \frac{72 + 4 \times 5 - 9}{80 + (3-1) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{75096}{83142} := \frac{7 \times (5-0+9-6)}{8^3 - 1^4 - 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{70245}{96831} := \frac{70 \times (2^4) - 5}{(9-6) \times 8^3 + 1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{72645}{98310} := \frac{7 + (2+6) \times 4 \times 5}{9 \times 8 \times 3 + 10} & \blacktriangleright \frac{75130}{84692} := \frac{7 + 51 - 3 + 0}{8 \times (4+6) - 9 \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{70362}{91854} := \frac{7 + 036^2}{9 \times (185+4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{72963}{81405} := \frac{7 - 2 + 963}{8 \times (140-5)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{75180}{92364} := \frac{7 \times 5^{1^8} + 0}{9 + 2 + 36 - 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{70623}{95418} := \frac{7 \times (062-3)}{9 \times (54+1 \times 8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{73062}{98154} := \frac{7 + 30 + 62}{9 + 8 \times 15 + 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{75240}{81396} := \frac{7 \times 5 \times 2 + 40}{8 + 13 \times 9 - 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{70914}{83625} := \frac{70 + 9 \times 1 \times 4}{8 \times (3+6 \times 2) + 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{73125}{80496} := \frac{(7-3+1^2)^5}{80 \times (49-6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{75240}{83961} := \frac{(7 \times 5 - 2) \times 40}{8^3 + 961} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{70965}{84132} := \frac{(70+96) \times 5}{8 \times (4+1)^3 - 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{73146}{80592} := \frac{7 \times 3 + 146}{8 \times (05+9 \times 2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{75421}{80396} := \frac{7 \times 54 + 2 - 1}{8 + 0396} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{71094}{82365} := \frac{7 \times 10 + 94}{8 + 2 + 36 \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{73152}{96480} := \frac{7 \times (31+5) + 2}{9 + 6 + 4 \times 80} & \blacktriangleright \frac{75609}{83142} := \frac{7 - 5 + 60 \times 9}{8 + 3 \times 14^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{71253}{96048} := \frac{7 \times (1+25) \times 3}{(96-04) \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{73485}{92016} := \frac{(7 \times 3 \times 4 + 8) \times 5}{9 \times 2^{01 \times 6}} & \blacktriangleright \frac{75648}{93120} := \frac{756 + 4 \times 8}{9 + 31^2 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{71280}{94365} := \frac{712 - 8 + 0}{943 - 6 - 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{73512}{94680} := \frac{7 \times 3^{5+1} + 2}{9^4 + 6 + 8 + 0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{76032}{91584} := \frac{7 \times 6 + 0 \times 3 + 2}{9 + 1 \times 5 \times 8 + 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{71309}{86254} := \frac{7^{1 \times 3} - 09}{(8 \times 6 \times 2 + 5) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{73682}{91504} := \frac{7^3 - 68 + 2}{(91-5) \times 04} & \blacktriangleright \frac{76041}{98532} := \frac{7 \times (6+04) + 1}{9 \times (8+5-3) + 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{71568}{90432} := \frac{7 \times (1+5 \times (6+8))}{90 \times (4+3) - 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{73905}{86412} := \frac{(7-3+9) \times 05}{(8+6 \times (4+1)) \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{76302}{91845} := \frac{7 \times 6^3 + 0 \times 2}{91 \times (8-4) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{71604}{85293} := \frac{7+1+604}{(8-5-2) \times 9^3} & \blacktriangleright \frac{74025}{96831} := \frac{(7+40) \times 25}{(9-6) \times 8^3 + 1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{76319}{84502} := \frac{7 \times (63+1) + 9}{8-4+502} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{71685}{92340} := \frac{7-1+6 \times 8+5}{9 \times 2^3 + 4+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{74025}{98136} := \frac{7 \times (40 \times 2 - 5)}{9 \times (81-3) - 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{76531}{82940} := \frac{7+65 \times 3+1}{(8^2-9) \times 4+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{71804}{95326} := \frac{(7+1 \times 80) \times 4}{(9 \times 5+32) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{74032}{86591} := \frac{7 \times 4^{0 \times 3+2}}{86+5 \times 9 \times 1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{76923}{84150} := \frac{7 \times (6 \times 92+3)}{(84+1) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{72063}{81954} := \frac{(7+2) \times 06-3}{8+1+9 \times 5+4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{74169}{85023} := \frac{(7 \times (4+1) + 6) \times 9}{8 \times 50 + 23} & \blacktriangleright \frac{76953}{82401} := \frac{(7+6+9) \times 5+3}{82+40-1} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{72063}{91845} := \frac{(7+2) \times 06-3}{(9+1 \times 8-4) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{74520}{83916} := \frac{(7 \times 4-5) \times 20}{(83-9) \times (1+6)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{78120}{96534} := \frac{7 \times (8+12) + 0}{9-6+5 \times 34} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{72354}{81690} := \frac{7^2 \times 3 - 54}{8+1+6+90} & \blacktriangleright \frac{74562}{89301} := \frac{7 \times 4 + 56 + 2}{8 \times 9 + 30 + 1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{78165}{90324} := \frac{7 \times (8+1^6) \times 5}{(90+3-2) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{72450}{93618} := \frac{(7-2)^4 - 50}{9^3 + 6 + 1 \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{74865}{90321} := \frac{7 - (4-8) \times 6 \times 5}{(90+3) \times 2 + 1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{78435}{92610} := \frac{7+84-3-5}{9 \times 2 \times 6 - 10} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{72450}{96831} := \frac{(7+2^4) \times 50}{(9-6) \times 8^3 + 1} & \blacktriangleright \frac{74925}{83106} := \frac{(7-4) \times 925}{(8^3+1) \times 06} & \blacktriangleright \frac{78540}{93126} := \frac{7 \times (8 \times 5 + 40)}{9^3 - 1 - 2^6} \end{array}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{78624}{93015} := \frac{7 \times 8 \times (6+2-4)}{9 \times 30 \times 1-5}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{79135}{82460} := \frac{7 \times (9+1 \times 3+5)}{8 \times 2 \times 4+60}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{79135}{86240} := \frac{79+1+3^5}{8 \times (6-2+40)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{79240}{86315} := \frac{(7+9-2) \times 4+0}{(8+6) \times (3+1)+5}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{7938}{102546} := \frac{7 \times (9-3+8)}{10+2 \times 5^4+6}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{79542}{83106} := \frac{7+9 \times 54-2}{8^3+1^{06}}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{7965}{102483} := \frac{7+9-6+5}{1+02 \times 4 \times 8 \times 3}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{80154}{97236} := \frac{8-01+54}{9-7+2 \times 36}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{80325}{91476} := \frac{(80+3+2) \times 5}{9-1+476}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{80325}{97461} := \frac{80-(3-2) \times 5}{(9-7) \times 46-1}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{81270}{93654} := \frac{(8+1^2) \times 70}{9^3+6-5-4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{81760}{92345} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 7 \times 60}{(9+2) \times 345}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{82365}{97104} := \frac{8+2+36 \times 5}{(9+7) \times (10+4)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{83457}{96102} := \frac{8-3+4+57}{96-10 \times 2}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{83506}{91274} := \frac{(8+35) \times 06}{9-1+274}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{83520}{97614} := \frac{(8+3+5) \times 020}{9 \times 7 \times 6 \times 1-4}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{84150}{96237} := \frac{(8+4-1) \times 50}{9+62 \times (3+7)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{84160}{95732} := \frac{8 \times (4+16)+0}{9 \times 5 \times (7-3)+2}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{84672}{90153} := \frac{(8+4 \times 6) \times 7 \times 2}{9 \times 01 \times 53}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{85137}{90624} := \frac{(8 \times 5-1) \times 37}{(90+6) \times 2^4}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{85241}{90376} := \frac{8+5 \times (2^4-1)}{9+03+76}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{85410}{97236} := \frac{(8+5) \times (4+1)+0}{9-7+2 \times 36}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{85671}{92340} := \frac{8 \times (5 \times 67-1)}{9 \times 2^3 \times 40}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{86125}{93704} := \frac{8+61 \times 2-5}{(9 \times 3+7) \times 04}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{86301}{97524} := \frac{8+6^3-01}{9 \times (7+5+2^4)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{86352}{97104} := \frac{(8 \times 6+3) \times 5+2}{9+7 \times 10 \times 4}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{86751}{92340} := \frac{(8+6-7) \times 51}{(92+3) \times 4+0}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{87120}{93456} := \frac{8 \times 7-1^2+0}{93-4-5 \times 6}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{87210}{96543} := \frac{(8+7^2) \times 10}{9-6+5^4+3}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{87462}{90513} := \frac{8-(7-46) \times 2}{90-5+1+3}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{9436}{102785} := \frac{94+3 \times 6}{10 \times 2 \times (7 \times 8+5)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{9576}{102438} := \frac{(9 \times 5-7) \times 6}{1+02438}$
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2.2 Four Digit's Numerator

$\blacktriangleright \frac{2349}{107856} := \frac{(2 \times 3)^4+9}{10 \times 7 \times 856}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{2349}{108576} := \frac{(2+3-4) \times 9}{(10-8)^5 \times (7+6)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{2376}{105984} := \frac{2+37-6}{(1-0+5 \times 9) \times 8 \times 4}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{2394}{106785} := \frac{2^3 \times 9+4}{1 \times 0678 \times 5}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{2394}{106875} := \frac{2 \times (39-4)}{(1 \times 06-8+7)^5}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{2394}{108756} := \frac{2^3+9+4}{10 \times 8 \times (7+5)-6}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{2457}{109863} := \frac{(2+4-5) \times 7}{1+(098+6) \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2574}{106938} := \frac{(2+5) \times (7+4)}{1069 \times 3-8}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{2673}{104895} := \frac{267-3}{10^4+8 \times 9 \times 5}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{2673}{105948} := \frac{26-7+3}{(10+5+94) \times 8}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{2739}{108564} := \frac{2 \times (7+3)-9}{(108-5+6) \times 4}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{2754}{106839} := \frac{2 \times 7+5 \times 4}{(10+6) \times 83-9}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{2754}{109836} := \frac{2 \times 7+5 \times 4}{(10+9 \times 8 \times 3) \times 6}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{2784}{105936} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 8+4}{10+(5+9^3) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2835}{109674} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 35}{1+09 \times (6+7^4)}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{2976}{103584} := \frac{2 \times 9+7+6}{10^3-5+84}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{3249}{108756} := \frac{32-4-9}{10+8 \times (7+5) \times 6}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{3458}{107692} := \frac{3 \times (4+5)+8}{1+(07 \times 6-9)^2}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{3458}{107926} := \frac{3 \times (4+5)-8}{10+7+9 \times 2^6}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{3564}{107892} := \frac{35-6+4}{107+892}$ $\blacktriangleright \frac{3564}{108972} := \frac{35-6+4}{1+08 \times 9 \times 7 \times 2}$
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$\blacktriangleright \frac{3564}{109728} := \frac{35 - 6 + 4}{(1 + 09 \times 7 \times 2) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4536}{109728} := \frac{45 + 3 - 6}{(1 + 09 \times 7 \times 2) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5967}{123084} := \frac{(5 \times 9 + 6) \times 7}{(1 + 230 \times 8) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{3645}{109872} := \frac{(3 + 6) \times 45}{109 \times 8 \times 7 \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4568}{123907} := \frac{(4 + 5 - 6) \times 8}{1^2 \times (3 + 90) \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5984}{120736} := \frac{(59 - 8) \times 4}{1 \times 2 \times (0 + 7^3 \times 6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{3654}{109872} := \frac{3 + 6 + 5 \times 4}{(1 + 09) \times 87 + 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4752}{103896} := \frac{4 - 7 + 5^2}{1 - (03 - 8) \times 96}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{6273}{104958} := \frac{62 - 7 \times 3}{(10 + 4) \times (9 + 5 \times 8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{3672}{104958} := \frac{3 + 67 + 2}{10 + 4^{9-5} \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4752}{103968} := \frac{4 \times (7 \times 5 - 2)}{10 \times 3 \times 96 + 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{6275}{108934} := \frac{62 - 7 - 5}{(1 + 08 \times 9 \times 3) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{3672}{109548} := \frac{3 - 6 + 7 + 2}{10 + 9 + 5 \times 4 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4823}{106795} := \frac{4 \times (8 - 2) - 3}{10 \times 6 \times 7 + 9 \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{6279}{103845} := \frac{6^2 + 7 + 9}{10 \times (3^{8-4} + 5)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{3725}{104896} := \frac{3 \times (7 - 2) \times 5}{(10 + 4 + 8) \times 96}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{4856}{120793} := \frac{4 \times (8 + 5 \times 6)}{1 + 20 \times 7 \times 9 \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{6327}{104895} := \frac{63 \times 2 + 7}{(1 + 048) \times 9 \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{3745}{108926} := \frac{(3 + 7) \times 4 - 5}{(10 - 8)^9 \times 2 - 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5073}{124689} := \frac{(50 + 7) \times 3}{(1 - 2 + 468) \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{6327}{105894} := \frac{6 + 3 \times 2 + 7}{10 + (5 + 8 \times 9) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{3864}{107295} := \frac{3 \times (8 + 6) \times 4}{10 + 7^2 \times 95}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5076}{123984} := \frac{5 + 07 \times 6}{12 \times (3 + 9) \times 8 - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{6345}{120978} := \frac{6 + 34 + 5}{(1 \times 2 + 09) \times 78}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{3970}{124658} := \frac{3 + 9 - 7 + 0}{1 + (2 + 4 + 6) \times (5 + 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5328}{104976} := \frac{5 \times 3^2 - 8}{(1 + 04 - 9 + 7)^6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{6384}{109725} := \frac{(6 + 3) \times 8 \times 4}{10 \times (97 + 2) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{3978}{104652} := \frac{3 + 9 - 7 + 8}{10 \times (4 + 6 \times 5) + 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5346}{107892} := \frac{5 - 3 \times (4 - 6)}{(10 - 7) \times (8 \times 9 + 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{6534}{109872} := \frac{6 \times (5^3 - 4)}{109 \times 8 \times 7 \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{3984}{106572} := \frac{3 + (9 - 8)^4}{(1 + 06) \times 5 + 72}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5463}{109872} := \frac{5^4 - 6 \times 3}{109 \times 8 \times 7 \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{6578}{120934} := \frac{6 + 5 + 7 + 8}{1 \times 2^{09} - 34}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{3984}{120765} := \frac{3 + 9 + 8 - 4}{(1 + 20 + 76) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5643}{109782} := \frac{56 - 4 + 3}{10 \times (97 + 8 + 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{6579}{103428} := \frac{6 + 5 \times (7 + 9)}{(1 + 03 \times 4)^2 \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{4263}{105987} := \frac{4 \times (2 + 6) - 3}{1 \times (05 + 98) \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5670}{123984} := \frac{5 + 670}{(12 + 3) \times 984}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{6725}{109483} := \frac{6 \times (7 - 2) - 5}{(1 + 09 \times 4) \times (8 + 3)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{4328}{107659} := \frac{(4 - 3 + 2) \times 8}{107 \times 6 - 5 \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5670}{124389} := \frac{5 \times 6 \times 7 + 0}{1 - 2 + 4^3 \times 8 \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{6732}{109854} := \frac{6 + 7 + 3^2}{10 + 9 + 85 \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{4329}{106587} := \frac{4 + 329}{(10 - 6)^5 \times 8 + 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5796}{103824} := \frac{5 \times (7 \times 9 + 6)}{103 \times (8^2 - 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{7038}{124695} := \frac{70 - 3 \times 8}{(1 + (24 - 6) \times 9) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{4536}{107289} := \frac{(4 + 5 + 3) \times 6}{107 \times 2 \times 8 - 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5936}{104728} := \frac{(59 - 3) \times 6}{104 \times (7^2 + 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{7254}{109368} := \frac{7 + 2 \times 5 - 4}{1 - 09 + 3 \times 68}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{4536}{107892} := \frac{45 + 3 - 6}{107 + 892}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5940}{123876} := \frac{59 - 4 + 0}{1 + (23 \times 8 + 7) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{7259}{106384} := \frac{7 \times (25 + 9)}{(106 + 3) \times (8 \times 4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{4536}{108297} := \frac{4 \times (5 + 3 - 6)}{(10 + 8) \times (2 + 9) - 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5967}{108324} := \frac{5 + 9 + 6 - 7}{108 + 32 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{7296}{103854} := \frac{7^2 + 9 + 6}{10^3 - 85 - 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{4536}{108972} := \frac{45 + 3 - 6}{1 + 08 \times 9 \times 7 \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{5967}{108342} := \frac{(5 \times 9 + 6) \times 7}{10 \times 8 \times 3^4 + 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{7298}{106354} := \frac{72 + 9 + 8}{1 + 06^{3+5-4}}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{7308}{125496} := \frac{7+30-8}{(1+2 \times (5+4 \times 9)) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{8256}{103974} := \frac{8 \times (2 \times 5 - 6)}{10+397-4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{9348}{107256} := \frac{93 \times 4 + 8}{10+725 \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{7326}{105894} := \frac{7+3+2 \times 6}{10+(5+8 \times 9) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{8294}{107536} := \frac{8 \times 2 + 9 + 4}{(1+07) \times (53-6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{9348}{107625} := \frac{93 \times 4 + 8}{1 \times 07 \times 625}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{7392}{105864} := \frac{7+3 \times (9-2)}{1+05 \times 8 \times (6+4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{8352}{104976} := \frac{83-5^2}{(1+04-9+7)^6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{9386}{120574} := \frac{9 \times 3 - 8 - 6}{(1+2) \times 057-4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{7450}{123968} := \frac{(7-4) \times 50}{(1+23) \times (96+8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{8532}{104976} := \frac{85-3 \times 2}{-1 \times 04 + 976}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{9483}{106275} := \frac{9+4 \times (8-3)}{10 \times (6+27)-5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{7650}{124389} := \frac{(7-6) \times 50}{(1+2) \times (4+3 \times 89)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{8624}{109375} := \frac{86^2-4}{10 \times 9375}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{9576}{104328} := \frac{9+5 \times 7-6}{10 \times 43-2 \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{7659}{104328} := \frac{(7+6) \times 5+9}{10^{4-3+2}+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{8639}{107254} := \frac{8+6+39}{10+72 \times (5+4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{9576}{108243} := \frac{9+5+7 \times 6}{10 \times 8^2-4-3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{7684}{123509} := \frac{(7 \times 6-8) \times 4}{1-2+3^5 \times 09}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{8643}{105927} := \frac{86 \times (4-3)}{1059+2-7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{9576}{124830} := \frac{(9-5) \times 7 \times 6}{((1+2)^4-8) \times 30}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{7695}{104328} := \frac{(7-6) \times 95}{10 \times 4 \times 32+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{8694}{103572} := \frac{(8+6+9) \times 4}{(1+03)^5+72}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{9584}{103627} := \frac{9-5+8+4}{10 \times (3+6) \times 2-7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{7695}{108243} := \frac{(7-6) \times 9 \times 5}{10 \times 8^2-4-3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{8736}{105924} := \frac{8 \times (7+3-6)}{(1 \times 05+92) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{9628}{105734} := \frac{9 \times 6^2+8}{10 \times 5 \times 73-4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{7695}{120384} := \frac{76+9+5}{(120 \times 3-8) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{8759}{103264} := \frac{8+7-5+9}{(10 \times (3+2)+6) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{9724}{105638} := \frac{9+7+2+4}{10+5+6^3+8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{7695}{123804} := \frac{(7-6) \times 9 \times 5}{(1+2^3) \times 80+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{8760}{123954} := \frac{(8-7) \times 60}{1+(23 \times 9+5) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{9768}{120435} := \frac{(9+7) \times 6-8}{(1+(2+04)^3) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{7695}{124830} := \frac{7+6-9+5}{1 \times 2+48 \times 3+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{9048}{125367} := \frac{(9+04) \times 8}{1+2^5 \times (3+6 \times 7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{9785}{124630} := \frac{97-8 \times 5}{(1-2+4)^6-3+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{7956}{108342} := \frac{7 \times (9-5)+6}{1+(08+3) \times 42}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{9048}{125736} := \frac{90-4 \times 8}{(1+2 \times 5) \times 7+3^6}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{7956}{123084} := \frac{7+9-5+6}{1+230+8 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{9234}{107568} := \frac{9+2 \times 3^4}{((10-7)^5+6) \times 8}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{7956}{124083} := \frac{7 \times 9-5-6}{1+2 \times (408-3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{9306}{124785} := \frac{930-6}{1 \times 2478 \times 5}$	

3 Pandigital Equivalent Selfie Fractions

3.1 2 Equivalent Blocks

• Five Digit's Numerator

$\blacktriangleright \frac{10248}{75396} := \frac{1 \times 02 + 4 + 8}{7^{5-3} + 9 \times 6}$	$:= \frac{10+24+8}{75+39 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10274}{69583} := \frac{(10-2) \times (7+4)}{6 \times (9+5) + 8^3}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 02^7 + 4}{69 \times (5+8) - 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10268}{94375} := \frac{(1+02) \times 68}{(9-4) \times 375}$	$:= \frac{10 \times (26+8)}{(9-4)^{3+7-5}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10275}{64938} := \frac{(1+02 \times 7) \times 5}{(6-4)^9 - 38}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 02 \times 75}{6+4+938}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{10296}{45738} := \frac{10-2+96}{457-3+8} := \frac{102+9 \times 6}{(4+5) \times 7 \times (3+8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10759}{32648} := \frac{1-07 \times (5-9)}{(3-2+6+4) \times 8} := \frac{10+(7-5)^9}{3 \times (2+64) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10296}{73458} := \frac{-1 \times 02+9 \times 6}{7^3+4 \times 5+8} := \frac{102+9 \times 6}{7 \times 3 \times (45+8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10764}{85293} := \frac{(10+7+6) \times 4}{(8-5-2) \times 9^3} := \frac{10 \times (7 \times 6+4)}{(8-5+2) \times 9^3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10368}{94752} := \frac{10 \times (3+6) \times 8}{94 \times 7 \times 5 \times 2} := \frac{1 \times 03 \times 6 \times 8}{94 \times (7+5+2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10836}{45279} := \frac{-1 \times 08+36}{(4-5+2 \times 7) \times 9} := \frac{(10 \times (8-3))+6}{(4-(5-27)) \times 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10374}{69825} := \frac{1-03+7 \times 4}{(6+9-8) \times 25} := \frac{1+03^7-4}{6 \times 98 \times 25}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10923}{75468} := \frac{1+09-2+3}{7+5+4+68} := \frac{1-(0-(9 \times (2 \times 3)))}{7+(5+(46 \times 8))}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{48762} := \frac{(10+3+9) \times 5}{4+8^{7-6+2}} := \frac{10 \times (39+5)}{48 \times (7+6^2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10935}{27648} := \frac{1 \times 09^3 \times 5}{2^7 \times 6 \times (4+8)} := \frac{10 \times (9-3)^5}{(2+7-6) \times 4^8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{62748} := \frac{10 \times (3 \times 9-5)}{(6 \times 27+4) \times 8} := \frac{10 \times (39+5)}{6^2 \times 74-8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10935}{27864} := \frac{1 \times 09^3 \times 5}{27 \times 86 \times 4} := \frac{1 \times 09 \times 3 \times 5}{(2+78+6) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{82467} := \frac{1^{03}+9+5}{8 \times (2 \times 4+6)+7} := \frac{(-1 \times 03+9) \times 5}{(8+2+4 \times 6) \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10935}{28674} := \frac{1+09+35}{2 \times (8 \times 6+7+4)} := \frac{1 \times 09 \times 3 \times 5}{((2+8 \times 6) \times 7)+4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{86724} := \frac{1+039-5}{(8+67-2) \times 4} := \frac{10 \times (3+9-5)}{8 \times (67+2+4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10935}{42768} := \frac{1+09+35}{4 \times 27+68} := \frac{1 \times 09 \times 3 \times 5}{4 \times (2^7+6)-8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10437}{25986} := \frac{(1 \times 04+3) \times 7}{2 \times (59+8-6)} := \frac{(10+4) \times 3 \times 7}{2 \times (5 \times (9 \times 8)+6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10935}{48276} := \frac{10+935}{4^{8-2}+76} := \frac{1 \times 09 \times 3 \times 5}{4-8 \times (2-76)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10458}{27639} := \frac{1 \times 04 \times 5+8}{2+7 \times (6+3)+9} := \frac{(1+04 \times 5) \times 8}{(2-76) \times (3-9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10962}{37845} := \frac{10 \times 9+6^2}{(3+7 \times (8+4)) \times 5} := \frac{(10 \times 9-6) \times 2}{(37-8) \times 4 \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10476}{82935} := \frac{(1^{04}+7) \times 6}{(82-9+3) \times 5} := \frac{(10-4) \times 7-6}{(8+2+9) \times 3 \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{10975}{32486} := \frac{(1+09) \times 7+5}{3 \times (2+(4+8) \times 6)} := \frac{10 \times (9-7)+5}{3 \times 24+8-6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10489}{67253} := \frac{(1^{04} \times 8+9)}{6+7+2^5 \times 3} := \frac{10+4 \times 8+9}{6 \times (7^2+5)+3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12360}{47895} := \frac{12 \times 3+60}{47 \times 8-9+5} := \frac{1-2-3+60}{4 \times 78-95}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10527}{86394} := \frac{(1+05)^2-7}{8+6 \times 39-4} := \frac{(10+5)^2+7}{8 \times (6 \times 39+4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12376}{85904} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 37-6}{8 \times 59-0 \times 4} := \frac{123+7+6}{8 \times 5+904}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10578}{32964} := \frac{1 \times 05 \times 7+8}{(32-9) \times 6-4} := \frac{10 \times (5 \times 7+8)}{(329+6) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12430}{65879} := \frac{1+2^4+3+0}{6+(5+8) \times 7+9} := \frac{(1-2+4) \times 30}{(6+5 \times 8+7) \times 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10584}{36792} := \frac{1+058+4}{3 \times 67+9 \times 2} := \frac{1^{05} \times 84}{36+(7+9)^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12584}{30976} := \frac{1-2-5+84}{3 \times (09-7)^6} := \frac{1+2^5+84}{3 \times (09+7) \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10584}{92736} := \frac{(10 \times 5-8) \times 4}{92 \times (7+3+6)} := \frac{105+84}{927+3^6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12584}{90376} := \frac{1^{25}+8 \times 4}{9+03 \times 76} := \frac{(1+2) \times 5+84}{9 \times (03+76)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10659}{34782} := \frac{1+065-9}{3 \times 4 \times (7+8)+2} := \frac{10+(6-5) \times 9}{3 \times (4 \times 7-8)+2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12597}{34086} := \frac{1+2 \times 5^{9-7}}{3 \times (40+8)-6} := \frac{(12 \times 5-9) \times 7}{3 \times 40 \times 8+6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10692}{35478} := \frac{10-6+9 \times 2}{3 \times (5 \times 4+7)-8} := \frac{1 \times 06 \times (9+2)}{3+(5 \times 4+7) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12705}{49368} := \frac{1^2 \times 7 \times 05}{4 \times (9-3) \times 6-8} := \frac{12 \times 7 \times 05}{4 \times (9-3) \times 68}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10692}{37584} := \frac{1 \times 06 \times (9+2)}{((3+7) \times 5+8) \times 4} := \frac{10 \times 6 \times (9+2)}{(3+7) \times 58 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12736}{58904} := \frac{(1 \times 2+7+3) \times 6}{5-(8-90) \times 4} := \frac{1 \times 2+7 \times 3 \times 6}{(58+90) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10692}{75438} := \frac{1+06+9+2}{(7 \times (5+4 \times 3))+8} := \frac{1+069+2}{(7+5) \times 43-8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12750}{34986} := \frac{(1+2 \times 7) \times 50}{3 \times 49 \times (8+6)} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 750}{(3+4) \times 98 \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{10726}{35984} := \frac{1+(07-2) \times 6}{(35-9) \times (8-4)} := \frac{10 \times 7-2-6}{3+5 \times (9+8 \times 4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{12765}{83490} := \frac{1+2 \times (7+6+5)}{83 \times 4-90} := \frac{12 \times (7+6 \times 5)}{8 \times (3+4 \times 90)}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{12789}{46305} := \frac{1+27-8+9}{(4 \times 6 - 3) \times 05} := \frac{1+2 \times 7+8 \times 9}{4+6+305}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13680}{29754} := \frac{1^{36} \times 80}{2 \times 97 - 5 \times 4} := \frac{13 \times 6 \times 80}{2 \times 9 \times 754}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12834}{57960} := \frac{1+2 \times (8+3+4)}{5 \times (7+9)+60} := \frac{1 \times 283 - 4}{(5+7+9) \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13702}{45968} := \frac{1 \times 370 + 2}{4 \times (5 \times 9 - 6) \times 8} := \frac{13 + 7^{02}}{(45-9) \times 6 - 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12903}{47685} := \frac{1-2+90+3}{4 \times (7+6 \times (8+5))} := \frac{1+2 \times 90+3}{(4+7+6) \times 8 \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13708}{45296} := \frac{13+7 \times 08}{4 \times (5-2+9 \times 6)} := \frac{1+3 \times (7+08)}{4+52+96}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12903}{48576} := \frac{1+(2+9) \times 03}{4 \times 8 \times (5-7+6)} := \frac{(-1+2 \times 9) \times 03}{4 \times 8 \times (5+7-6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13804}{59276} := \frac{1^3+80+4}{5-9 \times (2-7 \times 6)} := \frac{13+8-04}{5+9^2-7-6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12903}{57684} := \frac{(-1+2 \times 9) \times 03}{(5 \times (7+6) - 8) \times 4} := \frac{(12+90) \times 3}{57 \times 6 \times (8-4)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13824}{50976} := \frac{(1-3+8-2) \times 4}{50+9 \times (7-6)} := \frac{13 \times (8+2 \times 4)}{(50+9) \times (7+6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12908}{53476} := \frac{1^2 \times (90+8)}{5 \times 3^4+7-6} := \frac{1 \times 29 - 08}{5+3^4+7-6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13847}{29056} := \frac{1+(3+8) \times (4+7)}{2^{9+05}-6} := \frac{1+3^{8+4-7}}{2^9+0 \times 56}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12960}{43875} := \frac{1^2 \times 9+0}{(4^3+8-7) \times 5} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 96+0}{(43+87) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13950}{46872} := \frac{1^{39} \times 50}{4 \times (6+8+7) \times 2} := \frac{1 \times 39 \times 50}{468 \times 7 \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{12960}{47385} := \frac{1-29+60}{4-7+3 \times 8 \times 5} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 960}{4 \times (7^3+8) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13950}{48267} := \frac{(1 \times 3+9) \times 50}{4 \times (8 \times 2^6+7)} := \frac{1^{39} \times 50}{(4 \times 8 - 2) \times 6 - 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13065}{97284} := \frac{1^3 \times 065}{(9+7 \times 2 \times 8) \times 4} := \frac{130 \times (6-5)}{972-8+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13950}{64728} := \frac{(1 \times 3+9) \times 50}{6 \times (472-8)} := \frac{1^{39} \times 50}{(6 \times 4+7-2) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13076}{28954} := \frac{1^3+07+6}{(2 \times 8-9) \times 5-4} := \frac{1^3 \times 07 \times 6}{2-8+95+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13962}{50478} := \frac{1+3+(9-6)^2}{5 \times (04+7)-8} := \frac{(1-3+9 \times 6) \times 2}{(50+4-7) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13247}{96805} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times (2+4+7)}{(9+6 \times 8) \times 05} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 24-7}{(9+6+80) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13965}{27048} := \frac{1+3+96-5}{(27-04) \times 8} := \frac{(1 \times 3+9 \times 6) \times 5}{2 \times 70 \times 4-8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13294}{57086} := \frac{1-(3+2-9) \times 4}{5+70-8+6} := \frac{(1+3 \times (2+9)) \times 4}{570+8+6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13978}{25064} := \frac{1+3 \times 9-7+8}{2+5 \times (06+4)} := \frac{1 \times 3+9 \times 7-8}{2 \times (50+6-4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13467}{58290} := \frac{1^3 \times 4 \times 67}{5 \times 8 \times 29+0} := \frac{(1+3 \times 4) \times 67}{(5+8) \times 290}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13984}{25760} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times (9 \times 8+4)}{2 \times 5 \times 7 \times 6+0} := \frac{(1+398) \times 4}{(2+5) \times 7 \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13572}{46980} := \frac{1 \times 3+5+7-2}{46-9+8+0} := \frac{1+3 \times (5+7)+2}{46+9+80}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13986}{24570} := \frac{(1^3+9) \times 8-6}{(2-4) \times (5-70)} := \frac{1-3-9+8 \times 6}{2+(4+5) \times 7+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13572}{68904} := \frac{1-3+5+7^2}{6 \times (8+9 \times 04)} := \frac{1^3 \times 572}{(6+8 \times 90) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{13986}{25704} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 9 \times 8+6}{(2^5+70) \times 4} := \frac{1-3-9+8 \times 6}{(2 \times 5+7) \times 04}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13572}{80496} := \frac{1+3+5 \times (7-2)}{80-4+96} := \frac{1+3+5+7^2}{8 \times (049-6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14076}{23598} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 07+6}{2^3 \times 5+9+8} := \frac{(1+40-7) \times 6}{2 \times (3^5-9 \times 8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{27459} := \frac{1+3+60-8}{2 \times (7+45)+9} := \frac{(1 \times 3+60) \times 8}{(27 \times 4+5) \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14076}{89352} := \frac{1 \times 4+07 \times 6}{89 \times 3+5^2} := \frac{14 \times 07-6}{8 \times (9+(3+5)^2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{27945} := \frac{(-1+36) \times 08}{(2^7-9-4) \times 5} := \frac{(1 \times 3+60) \times 8}{(2 \times 7+9) \times 45}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14208}{69375} := \frac{14 \times 2^{08}}{693+7^5} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 20 \times 8}{(6+9-3-7)^5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{59724} := \frac{1+3+6+08}{59+(7-2) \times 4} := \frac{1 \times 36+0 \times 8}{5-9 \times (7-24)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14235}{67890} := \frac{1+(4-2+3) \times 5}{6 \times 7-8+90} := \frac{14 \times 2^3+5}{6 \times 78+90}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{94752} := \frac{1+3 \times 6+08}{9+4+7 \times 5^2} := \frac{1+3 \times 60+8}{94 \times (7+5+2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14280}{39576} := \frac{1+42-8+0}{3+95-7+6} := \frac{(1+4)^2+80}{3-(9-57) \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{13642}{89750} := \frac{13 \times 6-4+2}{(8+9-7) \times 50} := \frac{(1+3 \times 6) \times 42}{(8+97) \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14325}{87096} := \frac{1-4+3+25}{8 \times 7+096} := \frac{1 \times 43+2^5}{8 \times (7 \times 09-6)}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{14352}{87906} := \frac{1 \times 4^3 \times (5+2)}{8 \times 7^{9-06}} := \frac{(1-4+35)^2}{8 \times (790-6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14985}{27306} := \frac{1-4+98-5}{2^7+30+6} := \frac{(1+49) \times 8+5}{2+7+3^{06}}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14380}{95627} := \frac{1-4+3+80}{(9+5+62) \times 7} := \frac{(1+4) \times 3 \times 80}{95 \times 6 \times 2 \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14985}{62370} := \frac{1+49 \times (8-5)}{623-7+0} := \frac{((1+4) \times 9-8) \times 5}{(6+2+3) \times 70}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14382}{59670} := \frac{(1+4)^3+8 \times 2}{5 \times 9 \times (6+7)+0} := \frac{1+4 \times (3+8)+2}{5^{9-6}+70}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{14985}{73260} := \frac{1+4+9+8 \times 5}{7-3+260} := \frac{149+8+5}{732+60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14560}{39728} := \frac{1^4 \times 560}{(3 \times 9 \times 7+2) \times 8} := \frac{1+4+5+60}{3 \times (9 \times 7-2)+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15086}{74239} := \frac{(-1+5) \times 08+6}{7+4 \times (2+3) \times 9} := \frac{150+8-6}{742-3+9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14573}{82069} := \frac{1^4 \times (5 \times 7+3)}{8 \times 20+6 \times 9} := \frac{1 \times 4-5+7^3}{(8+206) \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15093}{48762} := \frac{1+50-9-3}{48+76+2} := \frac{1+50+9 \times 3}{4 \times (8-7+62)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14580}{23976} := \frac{1+4+5 \times 8+0}{2+3+9 \times 7+6} := \frac{1+4+5+80}{2^3 \times 9+76}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15093}{78624} := \frac{1+(5+09) \times 3}{7 \times 8 \times (6+2-4)} := \frac{1+50 \times (9-3)}{7 \times (8+6) \times 2^4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14580}{73629} := \frac{1^4 \times 5 \times 8+0}{7+3 \times 62+9} := \frac{(1 \times 4+5) \times 80}{7+3629}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15249}{70863} := \frac{1+5-2+4+9}{7+08 \times (6+3)} := \frac{(15-2+4) \times 9}{708+6-3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14625}{39780} := \frac{1+4+(6-2) \times 5}{3+9+7 \times 8+0} := \frac{(1 \times 4+6) \times 2 \times 5}{(3 \times 9+7) \times 8+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15308}{64792} := \frac{1 \times 5+30+8}{6 \times 4+79 \times 2} := \frac{(1+5) \times 30-8}{647+9^2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14628}{39750} := \frac{(1 \times 4+6)^2-8}{(3+9-7) \times 50} := \frac{(1+4 \times 6-2) \times 8}{(3+97) \times 5+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{26487} := \frac{1+53+09}{26-4+87} := \frac{1+5^3+0 \times 9}{2+6^{4-8+7}}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14630}{78925} := \frac{14-6+30}{(7+(8+9) \times 2) \times 5} := \frac{14 \times 6+30}{7+8 \times (9^2-5)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{28674} := \frac{1+53+09}{2 \times (8 \times 6+7+4)} := \frac{(1+5) \times 30+9}{(2+8 \times 6) \times 7+4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14637}{89250} := \frac{1-4+6 \times 3 \times 7}{(8+9-2) \times 50} := \frac{(1+4 \times 6) \times 3+7}{(8+92) \times 5+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{46872} := \frac{(1+5+3) \times 09}{4 \times (6 \times 8+7 \times 2)} := \frac{(15+3) \times 09}{4 \times (6+8 \times 7) \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14703}{59826} := \frac{(1+4 \times 7) \times 03}{(5+9 \times (8-2)) \times 6} := \frac{1+4 \times 70 \times 3}{59 \times (8^2-6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15408}{97263} := \frac{1^5 \times (40+8)}{(97-2+6) \times 3} := \frac{15 \times (40+8)}{9+72 \times 63}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14706}{83592} := \frac{1-(4-7) \times 06}{8+3+5+92} := \frac{(1+4) \times (70+6)}{8 \times 3 \times 5 \times 9 \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15480}{72369} := \frac{(1^5+4) \times 8+0}{7+(2+3 \times 6) \times 9} := \frac{1-5+4+80}{7-2+369}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14736}{90258} := \frac{1 \times 4+7+3-6}{9+02^5+8} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times (7+3-6)}{9 \times 02 \times 5+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15483}{70269} := \frac{1+5+4 \times (8-3)}{7^{02}+69} := \frac{1+5-4+8+3}{7-02+6 \times 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14739}{50286} := \frac{1 \times 4+7-3+9}{5 \times 02+8 \times 6} := \frac{(1+47+3) \times 9}{(5+02^8) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15496}{32780} := \frac{1-5-(4-9) \times 6}{3^2 \times 7-8+0} := \frac{1+54-9+6}{3+27+80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14798}{20536} := \frac{1+(4-7+9) \times 8}{2^{05}+36} := \frac{14 \times 7 \times (9-8)}{20 \times 5+36}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15498}{27306} := \frac{1+5 \times 4 \times 9+8}{27+306} := \frac{154+98}{2 \times (7+30) \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14805}{39762} := \frac{(-1^4+8) \times 05}{39-7+62} := \frac{(1 \times 4+80) \times 5}{3 \times (9 \times 7 \times 6-2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15687}{23904} := \frac{(1 \times 5+6-8) \times 7}{2 \times (3+9+04)} := \frac{1 \times 5 \times (6+8)-7}{2 \times (3+9) \times 04}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14826}{70953} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 8+2-6}{70+(9-5)^3} := \frac{(1+48) \times 2 \times 6}{70+(9+5)^3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15732}{64980} := \frac{1+5 \times (7-3)+2}{6 \times 4-9+80} := \frac{1+5 \times 73+2}{(6+4+9) \times 80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14952}{80367} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times (9-5-2)}{-8 \times 03+67} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times (9+5+2)}{8 \times (036+7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15738}{20496} := \frac{1+5 \times (7+3)-8}{2-0 \times 4+9 \times 6} := \frac{1-5 \times (7-3 \times 8)}{2^{04}+96}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14976}{30528} := \frac{1 \times 4+9+7+6}{3+05 \times (2+8)} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times (97-6)}{30 \times 5^2-8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15768}{24309} := \frac{15+7-6+8}{2-4+30+9} := \frac{(1 \times 5+7+6) \times 8}{2 \times (4 \times 30-9)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{14976}{83520} := \frac{(1-4+9+7) \times 6}{83 \times 5+20} := \frac{(1+4+9) \times 7+6}{(8 \times 3+5) \times 20}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{15840}{76923} := \frac{1 \times 5 \times 8 \times 4+0}{7 \times (6 \times 9 \times 2+3)} := \frac{1^5 \times 8 \times 40}{7 \times ((6+9)^2-3)}$

$\triangleright \frac{15876}{39042} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 87 + 6}{3^{9-04} - 2}$	$:= \frac{(15-8) \times (7 \times 6)}{3 + (90 \times (4 \times 2))}$	$\triangleright \frac{16830}{49572} := \frac{(1-6) \times (8-30)}{4 \times (95-7 \times 2)}$	$:= \frac{168-3+0}{495-7-2}$
$\triangleright \frac{15903}{26784} := \frac{1+59-03}{2+6 \times (7+8)+4}$	$:= \frac{1 \times ((5+90) \times 3)}{(2+(6+7)) \times (8 \times 4)}$	$\triangleright \frac{16842}{95037} := \frac{1 \times 6-8+4^2}{9 \times (5+03)+7}$	$:= \frac{(1+6) \times (8 \times 4+2)}{9 \times 50 \times 3-7}$
$\triangleright \frac{15903}{46872} := \frac{1+59-03}{4 \times (6+8+7) \times 2}$	$:= \frac{1-(5-(90 \times 3))}{(4 \times (6+(8-7)))^2}$	$\triangleright \frac{16920}{58374} := \frac{1^{69} \times 20}{5+8 \times (-3+7+4)}$	$:= \frac{1^6 \times 9 \times 20}{5+8 \times (3+74)}$
$\triangleright \frac{15903}{72846} := \frac{1+5+90-3}{(7+2 \times 8 \times 4) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{1-(5-903)}{(7 \times 2) + (8+(4^6))}$	$\triangleright \frac{16940}{35728} := \frac{1+69+40}{(3 \times 5+7 \times 2) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{(1+6 \times 9) \times 4+0}{(3+57-2) \times 8}$
$\triangleright \frac{15920}{84376} := \frac{(1-5+9) \times 2+0}{84-37+6}$	$:= \frac{((1^5)^9) \times 20}{(8 \times (4+(3+7))) - 6}$	$\triangleright \frac{17034}{92685} := \frac{1^7 \times 034}{(9+2 \times (6+8)) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{17 \times (0 \times 3+4)}{((9+2) \times 6+8) \times 5}$
$\triangleright \frac{15984}{20736} := \frac{1+5+(9+8) \times 4}{2^{07-3} \times 6}$	$:= \frac{1-5+9+8 \times 4}{2 \times (07-3) \times 6}$	$\triangleright \frac{17052}{69384} := \frac{17 \times (05)+2}{6 \times (9 \times 3+8 \times 4)}$	$:= \frac{1+(7+05)^2}{6 \times 9 \times (3+8)-4}$
$\triangleright \frac{16038}{27945} := \frac{1 \times 60 \times (3+8)}{2 \times 7 \times 9+4^5}$	$:= \frac{160+38}{(2+7 \times 9+4) \times 5}$	$\triangleright \frac{17085}{32964} := \frac{1^7 \times 085}{3 \times (2+9 \times 6)-4}$	$:= \frac{170 \times (8-5)}{(32+9) \times 6 \times 4}$
$\triangleright \frac{16038}{52974} := \frac{1-6+038}{5 \times 2+9 \times (7+4)}$	$:= \frac{160-3+8}{5+2^9+7 \times 4}$	$\triangleright \frac{17253}{86904} := \frac{1+72+5+3}{8 \times 6+90 \times 4}$	$:= \frac{(1+7)^2+5^3}{8 \times 6+904}$
$\triangleright \frac{16074}{23598} := \frac{1+6 \times 07+4}{2 \times 35-9+8}$	$:= \frac{(1+60) \times 7-4}{23+598}$	$\triangleright \frac{17280}{35964} := \frac{1^7 \times 2 \times 80}{3^5+9 \times (6+4)}$	$:= \frac{(1+7-2) \times 80}{35+964}$
$\triangleright \frac{16380}{27495} := \frac{1+63-8+0}{2-7+4+95}$	$:= \frac{(1+6) \times 3 \times 8+0}{2+(7+49) \times 5}$	$\triangleright \frac{17286}{30954} := \frac{1^7 \times 2 \times 86}{309-5+4}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 7-(2-8) \times 6}{3^{09-5}-4}$
$\triangleright \frac{16380}{49725} := \frac{1+63-8+0}{4-9+7 \times 25}$	$:= \frac{1+6-3+80}{4+((9+7)^2-5)}$	$\triangleright \frac{17309}{56482} := \frac{1 \times 7+3+09}{(5-6+4 \times 8) \times 2}$	$:= \frac{17+30-9}{56+4+8^2}$
$\triangleright \frac{16385}{49720} := \frac{(1 \times 6-3) \times 8+5}{4 \times (9-7+20)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 3+8 \times 5}{4 \times 9+7 \times 20}$	$\triangleright \frac{17395}{62480} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times (3+9-5)}{(6+2^4) \times 8+0}$	$:= \frac{(17-3) \times (9+5)}{624+80}$
$\triangleright \frac{16480}{75293} := \frac{1^6 \times 4 \times 80}{(7-5) \times (2+9^3)}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 4 \times 80}{(7+5) \times (2+9^3)}$	$\triangleright \frac{17458}{62930} := \frac{1 \times 7-4+5 \times 8}{62+93+0}$	$:= \frac{(1+7-4)^5+8}{(6-2) \times 930}$
$\triangleright \frac{16524}{37908} := \frac{1 \times 6+(5+2) \times 4}{3-7+90-8}$	$:= \frac{1+6^{5-2}+4}{3+7 \times 9 \times 08}$	$\triangleright \frac{17460}{92538} := \frac{1-7+46+0}{92+5 \times 3 \times 8}$	$:= \frac{17 \times (4+6)+0}{925-3 \times 8}$
$\triangleright \frac{16524}{38097} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times (5-2) \times 4}{(3+80) \times (9-7)}$	$:= \frac{(1+6+5)^2 \times 4}{(3+80) \times (9+7)}$	$\triangleright \frac{17493}{28560} := \frac{1^7+4 \times (9+3)}{2+(8+5) \times 6+0}$	$:= \frac{(1-7+4+9)^3}{(2+8) \times 56+0}$
$\triangleright \frac{16539}{87024} := \frac{(1+6 \times 5)^3+9}{8 \times 70^2 \times 4}$	$:= \frac{1+(6+5) \times 3 \times 9}{8 \times 70^2 \times 4}$	$\triangleright \frac{17496}{28350} := \frac{(1+7+4) \times 9 \times 6}{(2+8)^3+50}$	$:= \frac{(1-7 \times (4-9)) \times 6}{(2+8-3) \times 50}$
$\triangleright \frac{16587}{34920} := \frac{1^6+5 \times (8+7)}{(3-4+9) \times 20}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 65+87}{(3+4+9) \times 20}$	$\triangleright \frac{17520}{63948} := \frac{(1 \times 7-5) \times 20}{6 \times (3 \times 9-4)+8}$	$:= \frac{1+7+52+0}{6^3-9+4+8}$
$\triangleright \frac{16704}{25839} := \frac{1+67-04}{2+5+83+9}$	$:= \frac{16 \times 7 \times 04}{(2 \times 5 \times 8-3) \times 9}$	$\triangleright \frac{17589}{32604} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times (5+8)-9}{(32+6) \times 04}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 75+89}{(3+2) \times 60+4}$
$\triangleright \frac{16720}{35948} := \frac{1+6-7+20}{3 \times 5+9 \times 4-8}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times 7 \times 20}{3 \times (594+8)}$	$\triangleright \frac{17625}{39480} := \frac{1-7+6+25}{(3-9) \times 4+80}$	$:= \frac{(17+6+2) \times 5}{(39-4) \times 8+0}$
$\triangleright \frac{16758}{30429} := \frac{1-6+7 \times 5+8}{30 \times (4-2)+9}$	$:= \frac{(1+6) \times (7+5)-8}{30 \times 4+2 \times 9}$	$\triangleright \frac{17649}{30528} := \frac{1^7+64+9}{(3+05) \times 2 \times 8}$	$:= \frac{1+76 \times 4-9}{(3+05)^2 \times 8}$
$\triangleright \frac{16758}{93024} := \frac{1-(6-7-5) \times 8}{9 \times 30-2+4}$	$:= \frac{1+6+7 \times (5+8)}{9 \times 30 \times 2+4}$	$\triangleright \frac{17649}{53280} := \frac{1+7 \times (6 \times 4-9)}{(5-3+2) \times 80}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 7 \times 6 \times 4-9}{(5+3-2) \times 80}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{17649}{83250} := \frac{1+7 \times (6 \times 4 - 9)}{(8-3) \times 2 \times 50}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 7 + 64 \times 9}{(8+3) \times 250}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18759}{43602} := \frac{1 \times 8 + 7 + 59}{43 \times (6 - 02)}$	$:= \frac{(1+8) \times 75 - 9}{43 \times 6^{02}}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17682}{54309} := \frac{1-7-6+82}{5 \times (4+30+9)}$	$:= \frac{(1+(7+6) \times 8) \times 2}{5 \times (4 \times 30+9)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18792}{35640} := \frac{1+8 \times (7+9+2)}{35+6 \times 40}$	$:= \frac{18-7+9 \times 2}{3+56-4+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17802}{49536} := \frac{1 \times 7 + 8 \times 02}{49-5 \times (3-6)}$	$:= \frac{17 \times 8 + 02}{(49+5 \times 3) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18792}{43065} := \frac{1 \times (8+7+9) \times 2}{(4+3 \times 06) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{1+8+7 \times 9^2}{4 \times 30 \times (6+5)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17802}{93654} := \frac{1 \times 7 + 8 \times 02}{9 \times (3 \times 6 - 5) + 4}$	$:= \frac{17 \times 8 + 02}{9^3 + 6 - 5 - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18905}{72436} := \frac{1+89+05}{7 \times (2^4 + 36)}$	$:= \frac{18 \times (90+5)}{(7+2)^4 - 3 - 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17820}{43956} := \frac{1 \times (7+8) \times 2+0}{4 \times (3+9+5) + 6}$	$:= \frac{17+8+20}{4^3 - 9 + 56}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18954}{32760} := \frac{189+54}{(3-2) \times 7 \times 60}$	$:= \frac{18 \times 9 \times (5+4)}{3 \times 2 \times 7 \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17892}{45360} := \frac{1-7 \times (8-9 \times 2)}{4 \times 5 \times (3+6) + 0}$	$:= \frac{(1+7+8) \times 9 - 2}{4 \times 5 \times 3 \times 6 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18954}{60372} := \frac{1+8+9+5+4}{(6+037) \times 2}$	$:= \frac{1+8+9 \times 5 \times 4}{60 \times (3+7) + 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{17952}{60384} := \frac{(1+7+9+5) \times 2}{6 \times 03 \times 8 + 4}$	$:= \frac{1+79+52}{60+384}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18963}{42570} := \frac{1+8 \times (9-6+3)}{4 \times 2 \times 5 + 70}$	$:= \frac{(1-(8-9) \times 6)^3}{(4+2+5) \times 70}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18042}{39576} := \frac{180+4+2}{395+7+6}$	$:= \frac{1+8 \times 04 - 2}{3^{9-5} - 7 - 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{18975}{23460} := \frac{(1+8+9-7) \times 5}{2^{3+4} - 60}$	$:= \frac{(1+8 \times 9 - 7) \times 5}{2 \times 34 \times 6 + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18245}{73069} := \frac{1^{82} + 4^5}{(7-3)^{06} + 9}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 82 \times 4 \times 5}{(7+3^{06}) \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19026}{58437} := \frac{(1 \times 9 - 02) \times 6}{58+4^3+7}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 90 + 2^6}{5 \times 8 \times 4 \times 3 - 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18249}{75603} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 2 - 4 + 9}{(7 \times 5 - 6) \times 03}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 8 + 2 \times 4 - 9}{7 \times 5 - 6 + 0 \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19035}{42768} := \frac{1-9+03^5}{4 \times (2^7 + 6) - 8}$	$:= \frac{(1+90+3) \times 5}{4 \times (27+6) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18256}{94703} := \frac{(18-2 \times 5) \times 6}{(9+4+70) \times 3}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 8 \times 2 \times (5+6)}{(9+4) \times 70 + 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19260}{58743} := \frac{1^{92} \times 60}{5 \times (8+7 \times 4) + 3}$	$:= \frac{(1+9)^2 + 60}{5 \times 8 + 7 \times 4^3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18270}{35496} := \frac{1 \times 8 + 27 + 0}{3+5+4 \times (9+6)}$	$:= \frac{(1^8 + 2) \times 70}{(3+5 \times (4+9)) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19278}{46053} := \frac{1+9 \times 2 + 7 - 8}{46+0 \times 5 - 3}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 9 \times 2 \times 7 \times 8}{4 \times (605 - 3)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18354}{62790} := \frac{1 \times 8 + 3 \times 5 - 4}{(6+2) \times 7 + 9 + 0}$	$:= \frac{1 - 8^3 + 5^4}{6 \times (2+7 \times 9) + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19278}{56304} := \frac{1 \times 9 - 2 + 7 \times 8}{5 \times (6+30) + 4}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 9 \times (27+8)}{5 \times (6 \times 30 + 4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18396}{42705} := \frac{1+8 \times 3+9-6}{(4+2+7) \times 05}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 8 \times (3 \times 9 - 6)}{(4+2) \times 70 - 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19305}{78624} := \frac{(-1+9+3) \times 05}{7 \times 8 \times (6+2-4)}$	$:= \frac{(1-9+30) \times 5}{7 \times 8 \times (6-2+4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18450}{26937} := \frac{1^{84} \times 50}{2 \times (6+9 \times 3) + 7}$	$:= \frac{(1+8+4) \times 50}{2 \times 6 + 937}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19305}{86724} := \frac{(1+9+3) \times 05}{(8+67-2) \times 4}$	$:= \frac{(-1+9 \times 3) \times 05}{8 \times (67+2+4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18564}{39270} := \frac{(1 \times 8 + 5) \times (6 - 4)}{3 - 9 \times 2 + 70}$	$:= \frac{1+8+5+64}{3+92+70}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19345}{62780} := \frac{(1 \times 9 + 3) \times 4 + 5}{6^2 \times 7 - 80}$	$:= \frac{1+(9+3 \times 4) \times 5}{(6^2+7) \times 8 + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18603}{27495} := \frac{(1-8+60) \times 3}{(2 \times 7 \times 4 - 9) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 8 \times 60 - 3}{(2^7 + 4 + 9) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19350}{46827} := \frac{1^{93} \times 50}{46+82-7}$	$:= \frac{1^9 \times 3 \times 50}{46 \times 8 + 2 - 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18603}{29574} := \frac{(-1+8+6) \times 03}{2-9-5+74}$	$:= \frac{18+6^{03}}{2^9-5 \times 7 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19350}{87462} := \frac{1+9+3 \times 5+0}{87+4 \times 6+2}$	$:= \frac{(1^9+3) \times 50}{(8+74 \times 6) \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18640}{25397} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times (6+4) + 0}{25+(3+9) \times 7}$	$:= \frac{1^8 \times 6 \times 40}{(2+5)^3 - 9 - 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19432}{86750} := \frac{1-9+4+32}{8+67+50}$	$:= \frac{(1+9+4) \times 3 \times 2}{(8+67) \times 5 + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18675}{49302} := \frac{1+(8-6) \times (7+5)}{(4 \times 9 - 3) \times 02}$	$:= \frac{1+8+6+7 \times 5}{(4 \times 9 + 30) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19458}{37260} := \frac{1+9+45-8}{3 \times (7-2) \times 6+0}$	$:= \frac{1 \times 94 \times (5+8)}{(37+2) \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{18732}{49506} := \frac{1 \times 8 + 7 - 3 + 2}{4 \times 9 - 5 + 06}$	$:= \frac{(1-8+7^3) \times 2}{4 \times (9 \times 50 - 6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{19470}{62835} := \frac{19-4+7+0}{6+(2+8+3) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{1+94-7+0}{6-2+8 \times 35}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{19650}{42837} := \frac{1^{96} \times 50}{(42-8) \times 3 + 7} := \frac{(1^9+6) \times 50}{(4 \times 28-3) \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20961}{87543} := \frac{2+09+6 \times 1}{8+75-4 \times 3} := \frac{209-6+1}{(8 \times 7 \times 5+4) \times 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19720}{64583} := \frac{(1 \times 9-7) \times 20}{6 \times 4 \times 5+8+3} := \frac{(19-7) \times 20}{(6 \times 45-8) \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20967}{83145} := \frac{2 \times (-09+67)}{(8 \times 3-1) \times 4 \times 5} := \frac{20-9 \times (6-7)}{(8+3 \times (1+4)) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19760}{53248} := \frac{19+76+0}{5+3+248} := \frac{1^9 \times 760}{(5-3+2)^4 \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{20987}{64315} := \frac{20 \times 9-8 \times 7}{6 \times 4^3+1-5} := \frac{20+9 \times (8+7)}{(64+31) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19762}{84350} := \frac{1^9+7 \times 6-2}{(8 \times 4+3) \times 5+0} := \frac{1+9^{(7-6) \times 2}}{(8-4+3) \times 50}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21076}{43589} := \frac{2+10+76}{4-(3-5) \times 89} := \frac{2+1 \times 07 \times 6}{4+3-5+89}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19764}{28350} := \frac{(19+7 \times 6) \times 4}{(2+8-3) \times 50} := \frac{1 \times 976 \times 4}{2 \times 8 \times 350}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21356}{79804} := \frac{2-13+5 \times 6}{79-8+0 \times 4} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 35+6}{(79-8) \times 04}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19845}{67032} := \frac{1-9+8+45}{6+(70+3) \times 2} := \frac{(1+9) \times 8 \times (4+5)}{(6+70) \times 32}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21408}{76935} := \frac{2^{1-4+08}}{7-6 \times 9 \times (3-5)} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times (40+8)}{(7 \times 6+9 \times 3) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{19872}{35604} := \frac{(1 \times 9+8+7) \times 2}{3 \times 5 \times 6-04} := \frac{(1-9+8 \times 7) \times 2}{3 \times 56+04}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21480}{73569} := \frac{(2-1+4) \times 8+0}{73-5+69} := \frac{(2-1^4) \times 80}{7-3+5 \times 6 \times 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20167}{58394} := \frac{2 \times 01 \times 67}{(5+83+9) \times 4} := \frac{20 \times 1 \times 67}{5 \times 8 \times (3+94)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21504}{89376} := \frac{2^{1+5}+0 \times 4}{8 \times (9 \times 3+7)-6} := \frac{2^{1+5} \times 04}{(8+9-3) \times 76}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20196}{45738} := \frac{20-1+9+6}{4+5 \times 7+38} := \frac{201+9-6}{457-3+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21546}{79380} := \frac{2^{1^5+4}+6}{7 \times (9+3+8)+0} := \frac{2+1+5+4^6}{7 \times 9 \times 3 \times 80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20196}{83754} := \frac{20-1+9+6}{(8+3 \times 7) \times 5-4} := \frac{201+9-6}{837+5+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21580}{46397} := \frac{2 \times (1+5)+8+0}{4 \times (6 \times 3-9)+7} := \frac{2^{1 \times 5}+8+0}{(46-3) \times (9-7)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20349}{86751} := \frac{2 \times 03+4+9}{8+6 \times (7+5)+1} := \frac{2-0 \times 3+4 \times 9}{86+75+1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21603}{87549} := \frac{2-1+6 \times 03}{8^{7-5}+4+9} := \frac{(2-1) \times (60-3)}{8 \times 7 \times 5-49}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20367}{45198} := \frac{2 \times 03+67}{(4+5) \times (1+9+8)} := \frac{20+3 \times 6 \times 7}{4-5 \times (1-9) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21630}{84975} := \frac{2 \times (1+6) \times 3+0}{8 \times (4+9+7)+5} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 63+0}{(8+(4+9) \times 7) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20416}{39875} := \frac{2 \times 04 \times 16}{(3-9+8 \times 7) \times 5} := \frac{(20+4) \times 16}{3+9 \times (8+75)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21645}{39780} := \frac{2^{1^6+4}+5}{3+9+7 \times 8+0} := \frac{2^{1+6}+4 \times 5}{(3 \times 9+7) \times 8+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20468}{91375} := \frac{2 \times 046-8}{(9-1-3) \times 75} := \frac{2 \times 04 \times (6+8)}{(9+13 \times 7) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21708}{93465} := \frac{21+7+08}{9+3^4+65} := \frac{2 \times (170-8)}{93 \times (4+6+5)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20493}{51678} := \frac{2 \times (04+9)-3}{51+6-7+8} := \frac{2 \times (049-3)}{((5+1) \times 6-7) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21735}{40986} := \frac{2 \times (17-3) \times 5}{4 \times (09 \times 8-6)} := \frac{2+1 \times 73-5}{40+98-6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20514}{97836} := \frac{2 \times 05-1+4}{9+7 \times 8+3-6} := \frac{20+5+14}{97+83+6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21735}{96048} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 7 \times 3 \times 5}{960-4 \times 8} := \frac{(2+1^7) \times 35}{(9 \times 6+04) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20548}{97136} := \frac{2+05-4+8}{9+7+1 \times 36} := \frac{2-05 \times (4-8)}{97+13-6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21870}{35964} := \frac{(2+1) \times (8+7)+0}{3+5 \times (9+6)-4} := \frac{2+1+87+0}{(3 \times 5+9) \times 6+4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20618}{93574} := \frac{2 \times 06+1^8}{9-3+57-4} := \frac{2+06+18}{9+3 \times 5 \times 7+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{21945}{67830} := \frac{2 \times (1+9+4)+5}{(6 \times 7-8) \times 3+0} := \frac{(2+1 \times 9) \times (4+5)}{6 \times 7 \times 8-30}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20675}{98413} := \frac{(2 \times 06-7) \times 5}{(9+8) \times (4+1 \times 3)} := \frac{(2+06+7) \times 5}{9 \times 8 \times (4+1)-3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23016}{87954} := \frac{2 \times (30-16)}{8+79+5 \times 4} := \frac{2 \times (30+1)-6}{(8+7) \times (9+5)+4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20895}{36417} := \frac{(2 \times 08-9) \times 5}{3 \times 6 \times (4-1)+7} := \frac{(20+8) \times 9 \times 5}{3+6+(4-1)^7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23175}{90846} := \frac{2-3+1+75}{9 \times 08 \times 4+6} := \frac{2^3 \times 1 \times 75}{(90+8) \times 4 \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{20896}{43751} := \frac{2^{08-9+6}}{4^3+7-5+1} := \frac{(2+08) \times 9+6}{4 \times (3+7) \times 5+1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{23490}{78561} := \frac{(2+3-4) \times 90}{7 \times (8+5 \times (6+1))} := \frac{2 \times (3^4+9)+0}{7+85 \times (6+1)}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{23504}{78196} := \frac{(-2+3 \times 5) \times 04}{78-1+96} := \frac{2+3 \times 50+4}{7+8^{1 \times 9-6}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25830}{97416} := \frac{2-5+8+30}{97+41-6} := \frac{2^5+8+30}{(9+7 \times (4+1)) \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23598}{41607} := \frac{2 \times (3+5)+98}{(4-1) \times (60+7)} := \frac{(2+3+5+9) \times 8}{4 \times 1 \times (60+7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25839}{40716} := \frac{2+58-3 \times 9}{4 \times (07+1 \times 6)} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times (8 \times 3+9)}{40 \times (7+1 \times 6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23691}{54087} := \frac{2+3 \times (69+1)}{540-8 \times 7} := \frac{(2+3) \times (6 \times 9-1)}{5+40 \times (8+7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{25947}{31806} := \frac{(2-5+9) \times 4+7}{(3+1) \times 8+06} := \frac{2+5 \times (9-4+7)}{3-1+80-6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23715}{48960} := \frac{2 \times 3 \times (7-1)-5}{4-(8-9) \times 60} := \frac{2 \times (3-7 \times (1-5))}{4 \times (8+9)+60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{26071}{54839} := \frac{(-2+6) \times 07+1}{5+4 \times (8-3+9)} := \frac{2^6-07+1}{5^4-8^3+9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{23850}{41976} := \frac{2^3-8+50}{4-1+9+76} := \frac{(23-8) \times 5+0}{41+97-6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{26145}{38097} := \frac{2 \times (6+14)-5}{3 \times (80-9 \times 7)} := \frac{2+(6+1-4)^5}{3 \times (8+09) \times 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24138}{65709} := \frac{2-4 \times (1+3-8)}{65-7-09} := \frac{24+138}{6 \times (5+70)-9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{26145}{90387} := \frac{2 \times (6+14)-5}{90+38-7} := \frac{2+(6+1-4)^5}{903-8 \times 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24309}{57816} := \frac{2-4+30+9}{5+78-1+6} := \frac{24+309}{5+781+6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{26394}{87150} := \frac{2+6 \times (39-4)}{(8+7-1) \times 50} := \frac{2+(6+3) \times 94}{8 \times 7 \times 1 \times 50}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24570}{38961} := \frac{2 \times 45 \times 7+0}{38+961} := \frac{24 \times 5 \times 7+0}{(3+8)^{9-6}+1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{26785}{30194} := \frac{2+6+7+8 \times 5}{30-(1-9) \times 4} := \frac{2 \times (6 \times 7+8+5)}{30+1 \times 94}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24570}{83916} := \frac{2+(4+5) \times 7+0}{8 \times 3 \times 9 \times 1+6} := \frac{(2-4) \times (5-70)}{(83-9 \times 1) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{26815}{74390} := \frac{2 \times (68-1-5)}{74+3 \times 90} := \frac{2+6+8+15}{74+3+9+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24618}{59307} := \frac{2-4+6+18}{5 \times (9+3)-07} := \frac{2 \times (4+(6-1) \times 8)}{5+9 \times (30-7)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{26871}{43095} := \frac{2-6+8 \times 7+1}{4+3^{09-5}} := \frac{2 \times (68 \times 7+1)}{(4+30) \times 9 \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24795}{86130} := \frac{2-4+7+9+5}{8+61-3+0} := \frac{(2+4) \times 7-9+5}{8-6+130}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{26894}{31075} := \frac{2+(68-9) \times 4}{310-7 \times 5} := \frac{2^6 \times 8-9 \times 4}{(3+107) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{24957}{31860} := \frac{2 \times (4-9)+57}{3 \times 18+6+0} := \frac{2+4+95-7}{(3-1^8) \times 60}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{26910}{43875} := \frac{2+6 \times 9-10}{(4-3) \times (8+7) \times 5} := \frac{2 \times 69 \times 1+0}{(4+3+8)^{7-5}}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{25079}{84136} := \frac{2-50+79}{8 \times (4+1 \times 3+6)} := \frac{250+7-9}{841-3-6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{26910}{47385} := \frac{2+6 \times 9-10}{4 \times 7 \times 3-8+5} := \frac{2 \times 69 \times 1+0}{4^{7-3}-8-5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{25098}{71346} := \frac{250-9 \times 8}{(7+1+3) \times 46} := \frac{250+9+8}{713+46}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{26978}{35014} := \frac{(2-6) \times (9-7 \times 8)}{3^5+01^4} := \frac{2 \times (6 \times 9-7) \times 8}{(3^5+01) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{25197}{46308} := \frac{2 \times 5+1+9 \times 7}{4+6 \times (30-8)} := \frac{2+5 \times 1^9 \times 7}{4 \times (6+3+08)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27018}{63954} := \frac{2+70-1+8}{6^3-9-5 \times 4} := \frac{2 \times (70+1+8)}{6-(3-95) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{25317}{89046} := \frac{2+5 \times (3+1)+7}{(8+9-0 \times 4) \times 6} := \frac{253+1+7}{8+904+6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27054}{91683} := \frac{2+7+05+4}{9+1+6 \times 8+3} := \frac{270-54}{9^{1-6+8}+3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{25340}{78916} := \frac{25 \times 3-40}{7+(8+9 \times 1) \times 6} := \frac{25 \times (3+4)+0}{7-8+91 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27081}{93456} := \frac{2+7 \times (08-1)}{(9+3+4) \times (5+6)} := \frac{2+70+81}{(9+3) \times 4 \times (5+6)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{25389}{64701} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 3-8+9}{6+4+70-1} := \frac{(2+5+3 \times 8) \times 9}{6+4+701}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27318}{65940} := \frac{2 \times (7+3)+1+8}{65+9-4+0} := \frac{2 \times 73-1^8}{6 \times 59-4+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{25760}{93184} := \frac{25 \times 7-60}{(9+3+1) \times 8 \times 4} := \frac{2^5 \times 7+6+0}{(9 \times 3-1) \times 8 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27508}{39146} := \frac{2 \times (7+50+8)}{3-91 \times (4-6)} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 5+08}{3 \times 9+14 \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{25783}{96140} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 7-8-3}{(9 \times 6+1) \times 4+0} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times (7 \times 8+3)}{(9 \times 6+1) \times 40}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27531}{40698} := \frac{2+7 \times (5-3+1)}{40-6 \times (9-8)} := \frac{2 \times (7+5 \times 3+1)}{4 \times (06+9)+8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{25806}{43197} := \frac{2^5+8+06}{4+3+(1+9) \times 7} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 8+06}{(4+(3-1) \times 9) \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{27531}{96048} := \frac{2+7+5^3-1}{(9 \times 6+04) \times 8} := \frac{2 \times (7+5^3+1)}{960-4 \times 8}$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{27639}{41085} &:= \frac{2+7 \times (6+3)+9}{(4+10+8) \times 5} &:= \frac{2 \times 7 \times 6+3 \times 9}{(41-08) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{29184}{53760} &:= \frac{2 \times (9 \times 1 \times 8+4)}{5 \times (3-7+60)} &:= \frac{2 \times (91+8-4)}{5 \times (3+7+60)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27810}{43569} &:= \frac{2 \times (7+8 \times 1)+0}{4 \times (3+5+6)-9} &:= \frac{2+7+81+0}{4 \times 3 \times (5+6)+9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{29403}{67518} &:= \frac{2 \times 9 \times 4 \times 03}{(67-5 \times 1) \times 8} &:= \frac{294+03}{675-1+8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27819}{35406} &:= \frac{2 \times (7 \times 8-1^9)}{35 \times (4-0 \times 6)} &:= \frac{2 \times (7 \times 8+1+9)}{3 \times 54+06} & \blacktriangleright \frac{29408}{61573} &:= \frac{2^9-40 \times 8}{(6+1) \times 57+3} &:= \frac{2^{9+4-08}}{6+1+57+3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27846}{31059} &:= \frac{2 \times (7+8+4-6)}{(3+1) \times 05+9} &:= \frac{2 \times 7-8+46}{3+10+5 \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{29415}{68370} &:= \frac{2^{9-4 \times 1}+5}{6+8 \times (3+7)+0} &:= \frac{2+94+15}{6 \times 8+3 \times 70} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27863}{90145} &:= \frac{2 \times (7-8+6 \times 3)}{90+1 \times 4 \times 5} &:= \frac{2+7+(8-6)^3}{9+01+45} & \blacktriangleright \frac{29574}{38160} &:= \frac{2 \times (9+5)+7-4}{3 \times 8+16+0} &:= \frac{2 \times 9 \times (5 \times 7-4)}{(3+8+1) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27918}{53460} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 9-18}{5 \times (3 \times 4+6)+0} &:= \frac{2 \times (7+91)-8}{5 \times 3 \times 4 \times 6+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{29574}{80136} &:= \frac{2 \times 9 \times 5+7-4}{(8-01) \times 36} &:= \frac{2 \times (9+5)+7-4}{80+1-3+6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27930}{61845} &:= \frac{2 \times (79-30)}{(61-8) \times 4+5} &:= \frac{2 \times 7 \times (9-3)+0}{6+(1+8) \times 4 \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{29583}{46710} &:= \frac{2 \times (9+5+8-3)}{(4+6) \times (7-1)+0} &:= \frac{2 \times (9-5)+8+3}{(4+6-7) \times 10} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27963}{51480} &:= \frac{2+796 \times 3}{(51+4) \times 80} &:= \frac{2+79 \times (6-3)}{(51+4) \times 8+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{29601}{43758} &:= \frac{29-6 \times 01}{4+3 \times (7-5+8)} &:= \frac{2^9-6 \times 01}{4 \times 37 \times 5+8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{28063}{91574} &:= \frac{2+8+06+3}{9+1 \times 57-4} &:= \frac{28 \times (06)+3}{9 \times (1+57+4)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{29610}{58374} &:= \frac{29+6 \times 1+0}{5-8 \times (3-7-4)} &:= \frac{(2^9+6) \times 10}{(5 \times 8^3-7) \times 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{28341}{56079} &:= \frac{2+(8+3) \times 4+1}{5 \times 6+07 \times 9} &:= \frac{2+8 \times (34+1)}{560+7-9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{29610}{83754} &:= \frac{29+6 \times 1+0}{8+37+54} &:= \frac{2 \times (9+61)+0}{8 \times (3+7) \times 5-4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{28356}{91740} &:= \frac{2+8 \times (3-5+6)}{(9+1) \times (7+4)+0} &:= \frac{2+8+35+6}{91+74+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{29631}{85407} &:= \frac{2-9+6 \times (3+1)}{(8-5+4) \times 07} &:= \frac{2 \times (9-6+31)}{(8+5 \times 4) \times 07} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{28359}{60417} &:= \frac{2 \times (8+3+5)-9}{(6-0 \times 4+1) \times 7} &:= \frac{2^8-(3+5) \times 9}{(60-4 \times 1) \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{29678}{30514} &:= \frac{2+9 \times 6+7+8}{3+05 \times 14} &:= \frac{2 \times (9+6+7 \times 8)}{30 \times 5 \times 1-4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{28364}{90157} &:= \frac{2 \times (8+3 \times (6-4))}{90+1+5-7} &:= \frac{2^{8-3} \times 6+4}{(90-1^5) \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{29760}{41385} &:= \frac{2+9-7+60}{4 \times (13+8)+5} &:= \frac{2^{9-7+6}+0}{4 \times (1+3+85)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{28461}{37590} &:= \frac{2 \times (8 \times 4-6)+1}{(3-7) \times 5+90} &:= \frac{2 \times (8+46-1)}{(3+7) \times (5+9)+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{29853}{67410} &:= \frac{2+9+85-3}{6 \times 7 \times (4+1)+0} &:= \frac{((2+9) \times 8+5) \times 3}{(67-4) \times 10} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{28710}{63945} &:= \frac{2 \times (8-7+10)}{6+(3+9) \times 4-5} &:= \frac{2 \times (8 \times 7-1)+0}{(6+39+4) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30128}{95764} &:= \frac{(3-01) \times 28}{(9+5) \times (7+6)-4} &:= \frac{(30+12) \times 8}{(9+5) \times 76+4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{28740}{53169} &:= \frac{(2+8-7) \times 40}{53+169} &:= \frac{(2-8+7) \times 40}{5 \times (3+1)+6 \times 9} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30172}{98456} &:= \frac{3 \times (017+2)}{9 \times (8-4) \times 5+6} &:= \frac{30-1+7+2}{98-4+5 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{28917}{36450} &:= \frac{2 \times (8+9 \times 1) \times 7}{3 \times (6-4) \times 50} &:= \frac{(2 \times 8-9) \times 17}{3 \times (6+4) \times 5+0} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30195}{64782} &:= \frac{(3-01+9) \times 5}{6 \times (4 \times 7-8)-2} &:= \frac{(3+019) \times 5}{6 \times (47-8)+2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{28971}{43065} &:= \frac{2-8+9+71}{4+3 \times 06 \times 5} &:= \frac{(2+8 \times 9) \times 71}{4+30+6^5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30195}{86742} &:= \frac{(3-01+9) \times 5}{(8+67+4) \times 2} &:= \frac{30 \times 1 \times 9+5}{8 \times 6+742} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{29106}{37485} &:= \frac{(2+9 \times 1) \times 06}{3-7+4+85} &:= \frac{2^9+10+6}{(3 \times 7-4) \times 8 \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30294}{51678} &:= \frac{3 \times (-02+9)-4}{5 \times 1 \times 6+7-8} &:= \frac{(30 \times 2-9) \times 4}{5 \times (1+67)+8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{29150}{34768} &:= \frac{(2+9 \times 1) \times 50}{(3^4+7-6) \times 8} &:= \frac{(2+9) \times 150}{(34+7) \times 6 \times 8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30294}{86751} &:= \frac{3^{02}+9+4}{8 \times (6+7-5)-1} &:= \frac{30+2 \times 9-4}{8+67+51} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{29160}{35478} &:= \frac{(29+1) \times 6+0}{3+(5 \times 4+7) \times 8} &:= \frac{(2+9-1) \times 6+0}{3 \times (5 \times 4+7)-8} & \blacktriangleright \frac{30618}{97524} &:= \frac{3+06+18}{9-7 \times (5-2^4)} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 \times 6+18)}{(9+75) \times 2+4} \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{30672}{58149} := \frac{30-6+72}{(5+8+1) \times (4+9)} := \frac{(30-6) \times 7 \times 2}{(5+8 \times 1) \times 49}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{32076}{49815} := \frac{3 \times (2+07 \times 6)}{(49-8 \times 1) \times 5} := \frac{320+76}{(49-8) \times 15}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{30685}{47291} := \frac{(3+06+8) \times 5}{4+7 \times 2 \times 9+1} := \frac{30 \times (6+8) + 5}{4+7 \times (2+91)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{32085}{61479} := \frac{3 \times (20 \times 8-5)}{6 \times 147+9} := \frac{(3+20+8) \times 5}{6 \times (1+47)+9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{30846}{71295} := \frac{308+4+6}{7 \times (12+9) \times 5} := \frac{30 \times 8 \times 4-6}{7^{1 \times 2} \times 9 \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{32175}{60489} := \frac{3-2 \times (1-7-5)}{6+04 \times 8+9} := \frac{(3+2 \times 1) \times 7 \times 5}{60 \times 4+89}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{30857}{49162} := \frac{3 \times 08+5 \times 7}{4-9 \times (1-6) \times 2} := \frac{3^{0 \times 8+5}-7}{4 \times 91+6 \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{32184}{65709} := \frac{3 \times 2 \times 1 \times (8-4)}{65-7-09} := \frac{3 \times 2 \times (1+8) \times 4}{6 \times (5+70)-9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{30861}{74295} := \frac{3^{08-6+1}}{((7+4) \times 2-9) \times 5} := \frac{3^{0 \times 8+6-1}}{(7+4+2) \times 9 \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{32758}{61049} := \frac{3-2-7 \times (5-8)}{6-1+04 \times 9} := \frac{327-5+8}{6 \times 104-9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{30927}{48165} := \frac{3 \times 09 \times 2+7}{(4+8+1+6) \times 5} := \frac{3-09+2^7}{(4 \times 8 \times 1+6) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{32850}{47961} := \frac{(3^2-8) \times 50}{4+7 \times 9+6 \times 1} := \frac{(32+8) \times 5+0}{4 \times (79-6 \times 1)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{31027}{86549} := \frac{(3+10) \times 2-7}{8+(6-5+4) \times 9} := \frac{31-0 \times 2+7}{(8+6) \times 5+4 \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{32947}{80615} := \frac{(3-2+9) \times 4+7}{80+(6+1) \times 5} := \frac{(3+(2+9) \times 4) \times 7}{806-1^5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{31059}{82467} := \frac{(3+1) \times 05+9}{8-2+4+67} := \frac{3+10+5 \times 9}{(8+2 \times 4+6) \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{34056}{91872} := \frac{(3^4+05) \times 6}{(9-1) \times 87 \times 2} := \frac{3-40 \times (5-6)}{(9-(1-8) \times 7) \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{31209}{47586} := \frac{3+1209}{(4 \times 75+8) \times 6} := \frac{312-09}{(4 \times 7+5) \times (8+6)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{34506}{97128} := \frac{3 \times 4 \times 5-06}{(9+7+1+2) \times 8} := \frac{3^4-5+06}{9 \times (7 \times 12-8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{31280}{49657} := \frac{(3-1^2) \times 80}{4+(9-6)^5+7} := \frac{(3+1^2) \times 80}{496+5+7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{34821}{70596} := \frac{3 \times 48+2 \times 1}{70 \times 5-9 \times 6} := \frac{(3^4-8) \times (2+1)}{(70-5+9) \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{31407}{52896} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 4+07}{5^2-8+9+6} := \frac{3+(1+4) \times 07}{(5-2+8-9)^6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{34920}{57618} := \frac{(3 \times 4-9) \times 20}{5+76+18} := \frac{(3+4+9) \times 20}{(5 \times (7+6)+1) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{31482}{70596} := \frac{3 \times (14+8) \times 2}{70 \times 5-9 \times 6} := \frac{3 \times (1+4 \times 8) \times 2}{(70-5+9) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{34920}{71586} := \frac{(3 \times 4-9) \times 20}{71+58-6} := \frac{(3^4+9) \times 2+0}{71 \times 5+8+6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{31728}{45609} := \frac{3+1 \times 7-2+8}{4 \times 5-6+09} := \frac{3+17+28}{4+56+09}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{35061}{42978} := \frac{3 \times (5 \times 06+1)}{4+2 \times (9 \times 7-8)} := \frac{3 \times 50+6-1}{4+2 \times 97-8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{31806}{42579} := \frac{31 \times (8-06)}{4+2 \times 5 \times 7+9} := \frac{31 \times (8+06)}{4-2+579}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{35627}{48019} := \frac{3+5+6+2+7}{4+8+019} := \frac{3 \times 5+6 \times (2+7)}{4+80+1 \times 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{31850}{94276} := \frac{3 \times 1^8 \times 50}{(9^4-2-7) \times 6} := \frac{(3-1+8) \times 5+0}{9 \times 4 \times 2+76}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{35640}{87912} := \frac{3 \times 5 \times (6-4)+0}{8+7 \times 9+1+2} := \frac{3 \times 5+6 \times 40}{8 \times 79-1-2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{31860}{47259} := \frac{3 \times 18+6+0}{4 \times 7+2+59} := \frac{(3+1 \times 8) \times 60}{4^{7-2}-5 \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{35712}{94860} := \frac{(3+5) \times (7+1) \times 2}{(9-4) \times (8+60)} := \frac{((3+5) \times (7-1))^2}{(94+8) \times 60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{31875}{46920} := \frac{3 \times (18+7) \times 5}{4 \times 69 \times 2+0} := \frac{3 \times 1875}{46 \times 9 \times 20}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{35840}{97216} := \frac{3 \times 5 \times 8+40}{9 \times 7^2-1-6} := \frac{(3-5+8) \times 40}{9 \times (72+1)-6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{31924}{86750} := \frac{3-1+(9+2) \times 4}{8+67+50} := \frac{3+1+92-4}{(8+6 \times 7) \times 5+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{36018}{57942} := \frac{3 \times (6-01)+8}{5+7+9+4^2} := \frac{3 \times (60+1+8)}{5 \times (7 \times 9+4)-2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{31926}{80754} := \frac{3+19+2 \times 6}{80+7-5+4} := \frac{3-1+(9+2) \times 6}{(8+07 \times 5) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{36084}{79152} := \frac{360+8+4}{791+5^2} := \frac{3+60-8 \times 4}{7+9+1 \times 52}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{31947}{80562} := \frac{3+1 \times 9+4+7}{80-(5+6) \times 2} := \frac{319-4+7}{(80 \times 5+6) \times 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{36102}{47589} := \frac{(3+6) \times 10-2}{4 \times (7+5+8+9)} := \frac{36+10-2}{4-(7-5-8) \times 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{31968}{52704} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times (9+6)-8}{5+2 \times 7 \times 04} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 96+8}{(52+70) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{36108}{49572} := \frac{3+(6+1) \times 08}{(4 \times (9-5)-7)^2} := \frac{3^6-10 \times 8}{(4+95) \times (7+2)}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{36190}{75482} := \frac{3 \times (6-1) + 90}{75 + (4+8)^2} := \frac{36 - 1^{90}}{7 \times (5+4) + 8 + 2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{37926}{48510} := \frac{3 \times (7+9^2) - 6}{4 \times 85 - 10} := \frac{379 + 2 + 6}{485 + 10}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{36240}{75198} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 2 + 4 + 0}{7 + 5 - 1 + 9 \times 8} := \frac{(3 \times 6)^2 - 4 + 0}{(75 - 1 + 9) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38016}{47952} := \frac{3 + 80 - 1 + 6}{(4 \times 7 + 9) \times (5 - 2)} := \frac{(3+8) \times 016}{4 - 7 + 9 \times 5^2}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{36270}{45198} := \frac{3 - 6 - 2 + 70}{4 + 5 + 1 \times 9 \times 8} := \frac{3^6 - 2 \times 7 + 0}{(4+5) \times (1+98)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38165}{70942} := \frac{(3+8 \times 1 \times 6) \times 5}{(70+9) \times (4+2)} := \frac{(3+8+1 \times 6) \times 5}{(70+9) \times (4-2)}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{36270}{95418} := \frac{3 - 6 - 2 + 70}{9 \times (5 - 4 + 18)} := \frac{(3+62) \times 7 + 0}{9 \times (5^{4-1} + 8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38214}{60795} := \frac{3 \times 8 \times 2 \times 1 - 4}{60 - (7 - 9) \times 5} := \frac{3 + 82 - 1 + 4}{60 + (7 + 9) \times 5}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{3645}{102789} := \frac{(3 - 6 + 4) \times 5}{(1 + 02) \times (7 \times 8 - 9)} := \frac{(3+6-4) \times 5}{1 + 02 + 78 \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38571}{62049} := \frac{3 + 8 + 57 + 1}{62 + 049} := \frac{3 \times (8 \times 5 + 7 - 1)}{6 + (20 + 4) \times 9}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{36450}{71928} := \frac{3 \times (6 + 4) \times 5 + 0}{(7 + 1) \times (9 + 28)} := \frac{3 \times (6 - 4) \times 50}{((7 + 1) \times 9 + 2) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38617}{52049} := \frac{3 + 8 + 6 - 1 + 7}{5 + 2 \times (04 + 9)} := \frac{3 \times 8 \times (6 + 1) - 7}{52 \times 04 + 9}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{36519}{87024} := \frac{3 - 6 + 5 \times (1 + 9)}{8 \times 7 \times (-02 + 4)} := \frac{36 \times 5 - 1 + 9}{8 \times 7 \times 02 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38625}{41097} := \frac{(3 + 8 - 6) \times 25}{(4 + 10) \times 9 + 7} := \frac{(38 + 62) \times 5}{4 \times (10 + 9) \times 7}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{36540}{91872} := \frac{36 - 5 + 4 + 0}{9 - 1 + 8 + 72} := \frac{36 \times 5 - 40}{9 - (1 - 8) \times 7^2}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38625}{79104} := \frac{(3 + 8 - 6) \times 25}{(7 \times 9 + 1) \times 04} := \frac{(3 + 8 - 6)^{2+5}}{(7 + 9) \times 10^4}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{36740}{89512} := \frac{3 + (6 + 7) \times 4 + 0}{(8 \times 9 - 5 \times 1) \times 2} := \frac{(3 \times 6 - 7) \times 40}{8 \times (9 + 5^{1+2})}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38796}{51240} := \frac{3 \times (8 \times 7 - 9 + 6)}{5 \times 1 \times (2 + 40)} := \frac{38 \times 7 - 9 \times 6}{(5 + 1 \times 2) \times 40}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{36972}{50481} := \frac{3 + 6 \times 9 - 7 + 2}{(5 + 04) \times 8 - 1} := \frac{369 - 7 + 2}{504 - 8 + 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38916}{74025} := \frac{3 \times (89 + 1) + 6}{7 \times (40 \times 2 - 5)} := \frac{(3 + 89) \times 16}{7 \times 40 \times 2 \times 5}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{37062}{58149} := \frac{3 - 7 + 062}{5 + 81 - 4 + 9} := \frac{370 + 6^2}{(5 + 8 \times 1) \times 49}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{38916}{74520} := \frac{3 \times (89 - 1 + 6)}{(7 + 4 \times 5) \times 20} := \frac{(38 + 9) \times (1 + 6)}{7 \times 45 \times 2 + 0}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{37092}{56481} := \frac{37 + 09 - 2}{56 + 4 + 8 - 1} := \frac{(3 + 7 \times 09) \times 2}{5^{6-4} \times 8 + 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39074}{86521} := \frac{39 - 07 - 4}{8 + 6 \times (5 \times 2 - 1)} := \frac{39 + 07 - 4}{86 + 5 + 2 \times 1}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{37185}{46029} := \frac{37 \times 1^8 \times 5}{4 \times 60 - 2 - 9} := \frac{37 \times 18 \times 5}{(460 - 2) \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39105}{82476} := \frac{(3 + 9 - 1) \times 05}{8 \times 24 - 76} := \frac{(3 + 9 + 10) \times 5}{8 \times (2^4 + 7 + 6)}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{37206}{59148} := \frac{37 + 2 - 0 \times 6}{5 + 9 + 1 \times 48} := \frac{(3 + 7^2) \times 06}{(59 - 1 + 4) \times 8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39168}{57024} := \frac{3 + 9 + (1 + 6) \times 8}{5 + 70 + 24} := \frac{3 \times (9 \times 16 - 8)}{570 + 24}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{37260}{98415} := \frac{3 \times 72 + 60}{9^{8-4-1^5}} := \frac{(3 \times 7 + 2) \times 60}{9^{8-4-1} \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39204}{57618} := \frac{3 \times (92 - 04)}{5 \times 76 \times 1 + 8} := \frac{3 \times (9 \times 2 + 04)}{57 + (6 - 1) \times 8}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{37296}{51840} := \frac{37 \times (29 + 6)}{5 \times (1 + 8) \times 40} := \frac{37 \times (2 + 96)}{(5 + 1) \times 840}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39420}{61758} := \frac{3 \times (9 - 4) \times 2 + 0}{6 - 17 + 58} := \frac{3 \times (9 - 4) \times 20}{6 + (1 + 7) \times 58}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{37468}{91205} := \frac{3 - 7 + (4 + 6) \times 8}{9 \times 1 \times 20 + 5} := \frac{3 \times (74 - 6 + 8)}{(91 + 20) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39786}{45021} := \frac{(3 + 9 + 7) \times (8 - 6)}{45 - 02 \times 1} := \frac{3 + 97 + 8 + 6}{4 + 5^{02+1}}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{37584}{60291} := \frac{3 \times (7 + 5 + 8 - 4)}{60 + 2 \times 9 - 1} := \frac{3 \times (7 + 5) \times (8 + 4)}{602 + 91}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39861}{70452} := \frac{3 + 9 \times (8 + 6 \times 1)}{70 \times 4 - 52} := \frac{3 - 9 + 8 \times 6 + 1}{70 - 4 + 5 \times 2}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{37584}{60912} := \frac{(3 + 7 + 5) \times 8 - 4}{6 + 091 \times 2} := \frac{3 - 7 \times (5 - 8) \times 4}{60 + 9^{1 \times 2}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{39862}{45107} := \frac{(3 \times (9 + 8) + 6) \times 2}{4 + 5^{10-7}} := \frac{(3 \times 9 - 8) \times (6 + 2)}{4 \times (5 \times 10 - 7)}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{37620}{41895} := \frac{3 - 7 + 620}{(41 + 8) \times (9 + 5)} := \frac{37 \times 6 - 2 + 0}{((4 + 1) \times 8 + 9) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{40139}{56782} := \frac{40 + 1^{39}}{56 - (7 - 8) \times 2} := \frac{(40 + 1^3) \times 9}{5 \times (6 + 7) \times 8 + 2}$	
$\blacktriangleright \frac{37812}{50964} := \frac{37 - (8 - 1) \times 2}{50 - 9 - 6 - 4} := \frac{3 \times (7 + 8 + 1) - 2}{50 + (9 - 6) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{40152}{67398} := \frac{4 - 01 + 5^2}{6 - 7 - (3 - 9) \times 8} := \frac{4 + 01 \times 52}{6 - 7 - 3 + 98}$	

$\blacktriangleright \frac{40176}{85932} := \frac{(4+01+7) \times 6}{(8+5) \times (9+3) - 2} := \frac{(40+1+7) \times 6}{8 \times (5 \times 9 + 32)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{43068}{71295} := \frac{4+3 \times 06 \times 8}{7 \times (1+29+5)} := \frac{430+6+8}{7 \times (12+9) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{40293}{67518} := \frac{4+(02+9) \times 3}{67-5 \times 1^8} := \frac{40+293}{6 \times (75+18)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{43068}{79152} := \frac{4+3 \times 06 \times 8}{(7+9) \times (15+2)} := \frac{430+6+8}{791+5^2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{40321}{78659} := \frac{4^{03}-2-1}{7 \times (8+(6-5) \times 9)} := \frac{40 \times 3 + 2 \times 1}{7+8 \times 6 \times 5-9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{43092}{81567} := \frac{4+(3+09) \times 2}{8 \times 15-67} := \frac{4 \times (3+09+2)}{(8+1) \times (5+6)+7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{40365}{91287} := \frac{40 \times (3 \times 6-5)}{(9+12) \times 8 \times 7} := \frac{4 \times 03 \times 65}{9 \times 1 \times 28 \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{43168}{79520} := \frac{43-16-8}{7+(9+5) \times 2+0} := \frac{4^{3+1}+6 \times 8}{7 \times (9-5) \times 20}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{40736}{85291} := \frac{4+07 \times 36}{8+529-1} := \frac{4 \times (07+3+6)}{(8+5+2) \times 9-1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{43576}{92180} := \frac{4-3+57-6}{9+21+80} := \frac{4 \times ((3+5) \times (7+6))}{(9+2 \times 1) \times 80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{40917}{65823} := \frac{40-9-1-7}{6 \times 5+8+2-3} := \frac{40+91+7}{6 \times 5+8^2 \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{43602}{97851} := \frac{43 \times (6+02)}{97 \times 8-5+1} := \frac{4 \times (3^6+02)}{97^{-8+5}+1}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{40918}{62375} := \frac{409+1^8}{62 \times (3+7)+5} := \frac{40 \times (9-1)+8}{(6+2)^3-7-5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{43810}{92675} := \frac{4 \times (38+1)+0}{9+(2^6-7) \times 5} := \frac{4+38+10}{9+26+75}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{41256}{80793} := \frac{(4+1-2+5) \times 6}{8-07+93} := \frac{(4+1+2+5) \times 6}{(8 \times 07-9) \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{43956}{71280} := \frac{4 \times (3+9)-5-6}{(7-1) \times (2+8)+0} := \frac{4+(3+95) \times 6}{(7-1) \times 2 \times 80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{41283}{95076} := \frac{(4+1+28) \times 3}{(9 \times 5-07) \times 6} := \frac{4 \times (1+2^{8-3})}{(9-5) \times 076}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45129}{73680} := \frac{4+5 \times 1^2 \times 9}{(7-3+6) \times 8+0} := \frac{(45+1)^2-9}{(7+36) \times 80}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{41520}{78369} := \frac{4 \times 15+20}{7+8 \times (3+6+9)} := \frac{(41-5) \times 20}{(7+8 \times 3 \times 6) \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45612}{83079} := \frac{4 \times (5 \times 6+12)}{8+307-9} := \frac{4 \times 5 \times (6+1) \times 2}{8^3+07-9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{41580}{96327} := \frac{(4-1) \times 5 \times 8+0}{9 \times 6+32 \times 7} := \frac{(4-1^5) \times 80}{9 \times (63-2)+7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45630}{91728} := \frac{(45-6) \times 30}{(91-7) \times 28} := \frac{(4 \times 5+6) \times 30}{(91+7) \times 2 \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{41895}{63270} := \frac{4+1 \times 89+5}{6^3+2-70} := \frac{4+(18-9) \times 5}{(6+3)^2-7+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45630}{92781} := \frac{4 \times 5 \times (6-3)+0}{9+2 \times 7 \times 8+1} := \frac{4+56+30}{(9+2 \times 7) \times 8-1}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{42159}{70863} := \frac{4-2+1 \times 5 \times 9}{7+08 \times (6+3)} := \frac{(42+1 \times 5) \times 9}{708+6-3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{45936}{87120} := \frac{4 \times 5-9+3 \times 6}{8 \times 7-1^{20}} := \frac{4+5 \times (9+3)-6}{(8 \times 7-1) \times 2+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{42351}{98076} := \frac{4-2+35+1}{9+80-7+6} := \frac{4 \times (23 \times 5-1)}{980+76}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46170}{52839} := \frac{4 \times (6-1)+70}{5+2+8 \times (3+9)} := \frac{4+6+170}{5^2 \times 8-3+9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{42360}{75189} := \frac{4 \times (2+3 \times 6)+0}{7+5 \times (18+9)} := \frac{(4-2) \times 3 \times 60}{7 \times 5 \times 18+9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46170}{92853} := \frac{4 \times (6-1)+70}{(9-2) \times 8+5^3} := \frac{4+6+170}{(9^2-8) \times 5-3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{42803}{57691} := \frac{4+2 \times 8+03}{5 \times 7+6-9-1} := \frac{(4-2)^8-03}{5+7 \times 6 \times (9-1)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46170}{98325} := \frac{46+1+7+0}{(9+8+3 \times 2) \times 5} := \frac{4 \times (61-7)+0}{(98-3 \times 2) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{42813}{56079} := \frac{4 \times (2 \times 8+1)+3}{5 \times 6+07 \times 9} := \frac{428+1-3}{560+7-9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46320}{97851} := \frac{4 \times (6 \times 3+2)+0}{((9-7) \times 85)-1} := \frac{(4+6) \times 32+0}{(9 \times ((7+8) \times 5))+1}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{42891}{63075} := \frac{4^2+8+9+1}{(6-3+07) \times 5} := \frac{4-2-8+91}{(6 \times 3+07) \times 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46389}{72051} := \frac{4^{6-3}-8-9}{72-((0 \times 5)-1)} := \frac{4+(6 \times ((3 \times 8)-9))}{(7 \times 20)+(5+1)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{42930}{58671} := \frac{4 \times (2 \times 9-3)+0}{5 \times 8+6 \times 7 \times 1} := \frac{4+29-3+0}{5 \times 8-6+7 \times 1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46389}{75012} := \frac{4^{6-3}-8-9}{75+01^2} := \frac{4+6 \times (3 \times 8-9)}{(75+01) \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{43056}{91728} := \frac{4+30-5-6}{9-1+7^2-8} := \frac{430+5 \times 6}{(91+7) \times (2+8)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46501}{73892} := \frac{4 \times 6+50-1}{(7+3 \times (8+9)) \times 2} := \frac{4+(6+501)}{7 \times ((3 \times 8)+92)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{43065}{72819} := \frac{4 \times 30-65}{7 \times 2 \times 8-19} := \frac{(4+3 \times 06) \times 5}{7 \times 28-1-9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{46731}{82095} := \frac{46-7-3+1}{8 \times 20-95} := \frac{4+67+3 \times 1}{8+2 \times 09 \times 5}$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{46872}{90153} := \frac{4 \times (6+8+7) \times 2}{901+53} := \frac{4 \times (6 \times 8 + 7 \times 2)}{9 \times 01 \times 53} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{46893}{50127} := \frac{4+6-8+9 \times 3}{5-01+27} := \frac{(46-8-9) \times 3}{50 \times 1 \times 2-7} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{46893}{50721} := \frac{4-6+(8+9) \times 3}{5+07^2-1} := \frac{(4 \times 6-8-9)^3}{50 \times 7+21} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{47196}{53820} := \frac{4-7+(1+9) \times 6}{5 \times (3+8+2)+0} := \frac{(4+7-1+9) \times 6}{5 \times (3 \times 8+2)+0} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{47236}{91580} := \frac{4+7+2+36}{9+1+5+80} := \frac{(47+2) \times (3+6)}{9 \times (15+80)} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{47320}{81965} := \frac{47+3^2+0}{(8+1 \times 9) \times 6-5} := \frac{(4+7+3) \times 20}{8 \times (1+9) \times 6+5} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{47530}{86912} := \frac{4 \times 7 \times 5 \times 3+0}{8 \times 6 \times (9-1) \times 2} := \frac{4 \times (7 \times 5)^3+0}{(8 \times (69+1))^2} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{47539}{68012} := \frac{4 \times (7 \times 5-3)+9}{(6+8 \times 01)^2} := \frac{(4 \times 7 \times 5-3) \times 9}{(6 \times (8-01))^2} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{47601}{83592} := \frac{4 \times (7 \times 6-01)}{8 \times 3 \times (5+9-2)} := \frac{47-6 \times 01}{8 \times (3-5+9+2)} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{47610}{98325} := \frac{4+7 \times 6 \times 1+0}{9+83-2+5} := \frac{(4+7 \times 6) \times 10}{(98-3) \times 2 \times 5} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{48015}{63729} := \frac{(4 \times 8+01) \times 5}{6 \times (37-2)+9} := \frac{480+15}{6+3+72 \times 9} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{48195}{62370} := \frac{4+8+1+9-5}{6+23-7+0} := \frac{48-1+9-5}{62-3+7+0} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{48625}{73910} := \frac{4+8+6+2^5}{(7-3) \times (9+10)} := \frac{(4+86) \times 2-5}{7 \times (39-1)+0} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{48927}{63501} := \frac{4+8 \times (9+2 \times 7)}{(6-3)^5+01} := \frac{4 \times ((8+9)^2-7)}{6 \times (3^5+01)} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{48930}{51726} := \frac{4-8+9+30}{5-1+7+26} := \frac{4+8+93+0}{5 \times 17+26} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{49368}{57120} := \frac{49+(3+6) \times 8}{5 \times (7+1+20)} := \frac{4-9+368}{5 \times 7 \times 12+0} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{49518}{67203} := \frac{4+9 \times 5+1-8}{(6-7+20) \times 3} := \frac{49+5 \times (1-8)}{6+7+2 \times 03} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{4956}{102837} := \frac{4+(9-5) \times 6}{10^2 \times 83 \times 7} := \frac{4 \times (9+5) \times 6}{(10+2) \times 83 \times 7} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{49572}{83106} := \frac{4 \times (9+5 \times (7-2))}{(8+3 \times 10) \times 6} := \frac{(49-5) \times 7-2}{8^3+10^6} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{49815}{62370} := \frac{498-1-5}{623-7+0} := \frac{(49-8) \times 15}{(6+2+3) \times 70} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{49815}{62730} := \frac{4-9+81+5}{6 \times (2 \times 7+3)+0} := \frac{4 \times (9+(8+1) \times 5)}{62+7 \times 30} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\blacktriangleright \frac{49830}{56172} := \frac{(4-9) \times (8-30)}{(56-1+7) \times 2} := \frac{4+(9+8) \times 3+0}{5 \times (6-1+7)+2} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{50964}{87132} := \frac{50-9-6-4}{8 \times (7-1)+3+2} := \frac{50+(9-6) \times 4}{(8 \times 7 \times 1-3) \times 2} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{50976}{81243} := \frac{5 \times 09-7-6}{8 \times 1 \times (2+4)+3} := \frac{5+097-6}{81+24 \times 3} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{51408}{67932} := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 4+08}{6+7+(9+3) \times 2} := \frac{5 \times 14 \times 08}{6+7+9^3-2} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{51948}{60372} := \frac{51-9+4 \times 8}{(6+037) \times 2} := \frac{5-(1-9+4) \times 8}{60-3-7 \times 2} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{51984}{70623} := \frac{(5-1+9 \times 8) \times 4}{7 \times (062-3)} := \frac{5 \times 19 \times 8 \times 4}{70 \times (62-3)} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{52360}{91784} := \frac{5 \times (23-6)+0}{9+17 \times 8+4} := \frac{5 \times (2^3+60)}{9-1+7 \times 84} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{52614}{70389} := \frac{5 \times 2 \times (6+1)+4}{7+03+89} := \frac{52+61 \times 4}{7+0389} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{52710}{98643} := \frac{5 \times 2 \times 7 \times 10}{9+8+6^4-3} := \frac{(5-2) \times 7 \times 10}{9 \times (8 \times 6-4)-3} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{53276}{98140} := \frac{5-3-2+76}{(9-8) \times 140} := \frac{(5 \times 3+2) \times 76}{(9+8) \times 140} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{53284}{79061} := \frac{(5+3^2 \times 8) \times 4}{7+90 \times (6-1)} := \frac{532+84}{7+906+1} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{53289}{67041} := \frac{5-3+2+89}{6+70+41} := \frac{5+3^2+8+9}{(6+7) \times (04-1)} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{53460}{87912} := \frac{5+34+6+0}{8+7 \times 9+1+2} := \frac{5 \times (3 \times 4+6)+0}{8+7 \times (9+1) \times 2} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{53498}{72106} := \frac{5+3 \times 4+98}{7^2+106} := \frac{5 \times (3^4-9)+8}{7^2 \times 10+6} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{53742}{86190} := \frac{53 \times (7-4-2)}{86-1^9+0} := \frac{53 \times (7+4-2)}{(86-1) \times 9+0} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{53802}{67914} := \frac{5 \times 3 \times 8+02}{67+91-4} := \frac{53+8-0 \times 2}{67+9+1^4} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{53901}{87462} := \frac{53-9 \times 0 \times 1}{8-(7-46) \times 2} := \frac{53 \times (9-01)}{8 \times (74+6 \times 2)} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{54027}{86913} := \frac{5+4+02 \times 7}{8 \times 6-9+1-3} := \frac{5 \times (4^{02}+7)}{(8-6) \times 91+3} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{54237}{69810} := \frac{5 \times 4^2+3 \times 7}{(6+9) \times 8+10} := \frac{5^4+2-3 \times 7}{(6+9 \times 8) \times 10} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{54279}{63081} := \frac{5-4+27+9}{6+30+8-1} := \frac{5-4 \times (2-7) \times 9}{6^3-0 \times 8-1} \\ &\blacktriangleright \frac{54736}{90812} := \frac{5-4+7+36}{9+08^{1 \times 2}} := \frac{5+4+73+6}{(9 \times (08)+1) \times 2} \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{54780}{93126} := \frac{5+4-7+8+0}{9+3+1-2+6} := \frac{5+47+8+0}{(9+(3+1) \times 2) \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{60372}{85914} := \frac{6-0 \times 3+72}{8 \times (5+9)-1^4} := \frac{6 \times (03+7^2)}{(8 \times (5+9)-1) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{54960}{83127} := \frac{5 \times 4+9 \times 60}{(8+3 \times 1)^2 \times 7} := \frac{5 \times 4^{9-6}+0}{8^3-1-27}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{60523}{89741} := \frac{6 \times 05+2-3}{8 \times 9-7 \times 4-1} := \frac{60+(5-2)^3}{8 \times (9-7)^4+1}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{54963}{78012} := \frac{5+(4+9+6) \times 3}{7+(8+01)^2} := \frac{(5 \times 4 \times 9+6) \times 3}{780+12}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{60732}{84591} := \frac{(60-7+3) \times 2}{(8+4) \times (5+9-1)} := \frac{6 \times 07 \times 3 \times 2}{8 \times 45-9 \times 1}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{56079}{83214} := \frac{5-6+07 \times 9}{8+3 \times 2 \times 14} := \frac{560+7-9}{832-1 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{61074}{95823} := \frac{6+10 \times (7+4)}{(9+5) \times (8+2+3)} := \frac{6 \times (1+07 \times 4)}{(9 \times (5 \times (8-2))) + 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{56203}{94178} := \frac{5 \times (6+2)-03}{9-4+1+7 \times 8} := \frac{56+203}{9+417+8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{61537}{98042} := \frac{6+(1+5 \times 3) \times 7}{(98-04) \times 2} := \frac{(6+1 \times 53) \times 7}{(9+80 \times 4) \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{56278}{90341} := \frac{56 \times 2+78}{9 \times 034-1} := \frac{(5 \times 6+27) \times 8}{9^{03}+4-1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{62478}{90513} := \frac{6 \times ((2+(4+7)) \times 8)}{905-(1^3)} := \frac{(6+2-4) \times 78}{90 \times 5-1+3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{56472}{90138} := \frac{5-6+4+7^2}{90+1^3-8} := \frac{56 \times (4+7+2)}{90 \times 13-8}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{62913}{80754} := \frac{6 \times (2+9)+1^3}{80+7-5+4} := \frac{6+2^{9+1-3}}{(8+07 \times 5) \times 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{56481}{92730} := \frac{5^{6-4} \times 8+1}{(9 \times 2-7) \times 30} := \frac{56+4+8-1}{(9+2) \times (7+3)+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63074}{95128} := \frac{6 \times 3 \times 07-4}{(95+1) \times 2-8} := \frac{6^3+07 \times 4}{(9 \times 5+1^2) \times 8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{56490}{71823} := \frac{5 \times (6+4 \times 9)+0}{(7+1 \times 82) \times 3} := \frac{5 \times (64+90)}{7+18^2 \times 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63279}{84105} := \frac{(6+3 \times 2) \times 79}{84 \times (10+5)} := \frac{6-3 \times (2-79)}{8 \times 4 \times 10-5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{57132}{86940} := \frac{5+7+13-2}{8 \times 6-9-4+0} := \frac{(5+(7-1) \times 3) \times 2}{(8+6) \times (9-4)+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63420}{75198} := \frac{6 \times 3 \times 4-2+0}{7+5-1+9 \times 8} := \frac{(6 \times 3-4) \times 20}{(7 \times 5+1) \times 9+8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{57216}{84930} := \frac{(5 \times 7-2-1) \times 6}{8 \times 4 \times 9-3+0} := \frac{5 \times (7^2+1)+6}{8+4 \times 93+0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63549}{80127} := \frac{(6-3) \times 5 \times 4+9}{80+1^2 \times 7} := \frac{6-(3-5) \times 4+9}{8+(01+2) \times 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{57461}{82309} := \frac{5+7+4 \times 6+1}{8+(2+3) \times 09} := \frac{(5 \times 7-4) \times 6-1}{8 \times (2+30)+9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63720}{94518} := \frac{(6+3 \times 7) \times 20}{(94-5) \times (1+8)} := \frac{6^3 \times (7-2)+0}{(94-5) \times 18}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{57834}{92106} := \frac{5+7+8+34}{92-1 \times 06} := \frac{(5-7+8-3)^4}{9+2 \times 10 \times 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{63950}{74182} := \frac{6+3-9+50}{(7+4+18) \times 2} := \frac{(6+39) \times 5+0}{7^{4-1}-82}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{58401}{93627} := \frac{58+4+01}{9 \times 3 \times (6-2)-7} := \frac{5 \times 8+401}{(93+6+2) \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{64152}{70389} := \frac{6 \times 4 \times 1 \times (5-2)}{7-0 \times 3+8 \times 9} := \frac{(6 \times (4-1))^{5-2}}{(703+8) \times 9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{58473}{96120} := \frac{(5+8-4) \times 73}{9 \times 6 \times 1 \times 20} := \frac{(58-4) \times 73}{9 \times 6 \times 120}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{64320}{71958} := \frac{(6-4) \times 320}{719+5-8} := \frac{64 \times (3+2)+0}{7 \times (1+9) \times 5+8}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{59102}{78463} := \frac{59+1-02}{78-4+6-3} := \frac{5+9+102}{7 \times (8-4+6 \times 3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{64370}{98125} := \frac{6 \times (4+37)+0}{(9 \times 8+1+2) \times 5} := \frac{6 \times 43+70}{(98+1 \times 2) \times 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{59102}{87634} := \frac{59+1-02}{87+6-3-4} := \frac{5+9+102}{8 \times 7 \times (6-3)+4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{64832}{90157} := \frac{(6+4-8) \times 32}{90+1+5-7} := \frac{64 \times (8-3+2)}{(90-1^5) \times 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{59124}{67083} := \frac{(5+9-1^2) \times 4}{6+7 \times 08-3} := \frac{(5+9-1) \times 24}{6 \times (7 \times 08+3)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{64872}{93015} := \frac{64+8 \times (7+2)}{(9+30 \times 1) \times 5} := \frac{6 \times (4-8+72)}{(9+30) \times 15}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{59280}{67431} := \frac{5 \times 9 \times 2 \times 8+0}{(6+7) \times (4^3-1)} := \frac{(5+9) \times 280}{6 \times 743+1}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{65340}{91872} := \frac{6 \times (5 \times 3+40)}{(9-1) \times (8 \times 7+2)} := \frac{6 \times (5^3+40)}{(9-1) \times 87 \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{59328}{76014} := \frac{5-9 \times (3+2-8)}{7 \times 6-01^4} := \frac{5 \times (9+3) \times 2+8}{(7 \times 6-01) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{65372}{94180} := \frac{6+5^3-72}{9-4+1 \times 80} := \frac{(6+53) \times (7+2)}{9 \times (4+1+80)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{59831}{60724} := \frac{5+98+31}{60+72+4} := \frac{5+98 \times (3-1)}{(60-7-2) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{65379}{80142} := \frac{6+5+3+79}{8 \times 014+2} := \frac{6+5 \times (3-7+9)}{8 \times (01+4)-2}$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{6549}{102837} := \frac{6 \times 5 \times 4 - 9}{(1 + 02) \times 83 \times 7} := \frac{6 - 5 + 4 \times 9}{1^{02} \times 83 \times 7}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{73548}{96021} := \frac{7 + 3 + 54 + 8}{96 - 02 \times 1} := \frac{7 \times 35 \times 4 - 8}{9 + 60 \times 21}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{65807}{91324} := \frac{(-6 + 5 + 8) \times 07}{(9 - 1 + 3^2) \times 4} := \frac{6 + 5 + 80 + 7}{9 - 1 + 32 \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{74025}{91368} := \frac{7 \times (40 + 2 \times 5)}{9 \times 1^3 \times 6 \times 8} := \frac{7 \times (40 \times 2 - 5)}{9 \times (1 + 3 + 68)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{65984}{73201} := \frac{(6 + 5 - 9) \times 8 \times 4}{73 - 2 \times 01} := \frac{6 \times (5 + 9 + 8) - 4}{7^3 - 201}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{74529}{80613} := \frac{7^{4+5+2-9}}{8 \times (06 + 1) - 3} := \frac{7 \times (4 + 5 - 2) \times 9}{80 \times 6 \times 1 - 3}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{67095}{82431} := \frac{6 \times 7 \times (0 \times 9 + 5)}{(82 + 4) \times 3 \times 1} := \frac{6 \times 70 \times (9 - 5)}{8 \times (2 + 4^{3+1})}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{75816}{92340} := \frac{7 \times (5 + 8 - 1) - 6}{9 + 2 \times (3 + 40)} := \frac{(7 + 5 \times (8 + 1)) \times 6}{(92 + 3) \times 4 + 0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{67284}{90513} := \frac{6 \times 7 \times 2 \times (8 - 4)}{90 \times 5 - 1 + 3} := \frac{6 \times 7 \times 2^{8-4}}{905 - 1^3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{76384}{91520} := \frac{7 \times 6 \times (3 + 8) - 4}{(9 + 1) \times 52 + 0} := \frac{7 + 6 \times (3 + 8 \times 4)}{(9 - 1 + 5) \times 20}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{67314}{80259} := \frac{6 - 7 + 31 - 4}{8 + 02^5 - 9} := \frac{673 - 1 + 4}{802 - 5 + 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{76593}{81024} := \frac{(76 + 5 \times 9) \times 3}{8 \times (10 + 2) \times 4} := \frac{(76 + 5) \times 9 - 3}{8 \times (10^2 - 4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{68145}{73920} := \frac{6 + 8 + 1 \times 45}{7 \times (3 + 9) - 20} := \frac{6 \times 8 + 14 \times 5}{(73 - 9) \times 2 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{78120}{93465} := \frac{7 \times 8 \times 1^{20}}{9 - 3 - 4 + 65} := \frac{7 \times 8 \times 1 \times 2 + 0}{93 + 46 - 5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{68475}{92130} := \frac{68 + 47 - 5}{9 \times 2 + 130} := \frac{6 + 84 + 75}{9 + 213 + 0}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{78650}{91234} := \frac{(7 - 8 + 6) \times 5 + 0}{9 + 1 + 23 - 4} := \frac{7 + 8 \times 6 - 5 + 0}{9 \times (1 + 2 + 3) + 4}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{69175}{80243} := \frac{(6 - 9 + 1 + 7) \times 5}{8 + 024 - 3} := \frac{6 \times (9 - 1) \times 75}{80 + 2^{4 \times 3}}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{79236}{80514} := \frac{7 \times (9 + 2 - 3) + 6}{8 + 051 + 4} := \frac{7 \times (9 + 2) + 3^6}{805 + 14}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{70561}{84329} := \frac{7 \times 05 + 6 \times 1}{8 \times (4 + 3 - 2) + 9} := \frac{70 + 5 + 6 + 1}{8 + (4 + 3 \times 2) \times 9}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{81567}{92340} := \frac{8 \times 15 - 67}{(9 + 2 \times 3) \times 4 + 0} := \frac{(8 + 1) \times (5 + 6) + 7}{(9 - 2 \times 3) \times 40}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{70623}{85491} := \frac{(7 + 06 \times 2) \times 3}{8 \times 5 \times 4 - 91} := \frac{(70 + 6) \times 2^3}{8 \times (5 - 4 + 91)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{81765}{92430} := \frac{8 + 1 + 7 + 6 \times 5}{9 \times 2 + 4 + 30} := \frac{(8 - 1) \times 7 \times 6 + 5}{92 \times 4 - 30}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{70623}{98154} := \frac{(7 \times (06 + 2) + 3)}{9 \times (8 + 1) + 5 - 4} := \frac{70 + 6 \times 2^3}{(9 - 8 \times (1 - 5)) \times 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{82160}{93457} := \frac{8^2 + 16 + 0}{(9 + 3 - 4 + 5) \times 7} := \frac{(8 + 2) \times 16 + 0}{(9 - 3 + 4 \times 5) \times 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{70914}{85632} := \frac{70 + 9 \times 1 \times 4}{8 \times (5 + 6 + 3 + 2)} := \frac{7 + 091 \times 4}{8 \times 56 \times (3 - 2)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{83160}{94752} := \frac{8 - 3 + 160}{9 + 4 + 7 \times 5^2} := \frac{831 - 6 + 0}{94 \times (7 + 5 - 2)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{71208}{93654} := \frac{7 \times 12 + 08}{9 \times (3 \times 6 - 5) + 4} := \frac{(71 - 2) \times 08}{9^3 + 6 - 5 - 4}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{84321}{90567} := \frac{8 + 43 + 2 + 1}{9 + 056 - 7} := \frac{8 \times (4 + 3 \times 2) + 1}{9 \times 05 + 6 \times 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{71230}{98465} := \frac{7 - 1 - 2 + 30}{9 \times (8 - 4) + 6 + 5} := \frac{7 + 1 + 2 \times 30}{9 + 8 \times (4 + 6) + 5}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{86437}{92105} := \frac{(8 + 6 + 4) \times 3 + 7}{(9 - 2) \times 10 - 5} := \frac{(8^6 - 4 - 3) \times 7}{(92 - 1) \times 05}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{71495}{83260} := \frac{71 + 49 \times 5}{8 + 3 \times 2 \times 60} := \frac{7 + (1 + 4)^{9-5}}{8 \times (32 + 60)}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{87241}{96305} := \frac{8 + 72 - 4 + 1}{(9 - 6) \times 30 - 5} := \frac{(8 \times 7 + 2) \times 4 - 1}{(9 \times 6 - 3) \times 05}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{71820}{94563} := \frac{(7 - 1) \times (8 + 2) + 0}{94 - 5 \times (6 - 3)} := \frac{718 + 2 + 0}{945 + 6 - 3}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{87543}{92016} := \frac{8 - 7 \times (5 - 43)}{9 \times 2 \times 016} := \frac{8 \times (7 \times 5 \times 4 - 3)}{9 \times 2^{01+6}}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{73158}{92064} := \frac{7^3 \times 1 + 5 + 8}{(9 - 2) \times 064} := \frac{7^{3-1} + 5 \times 8}{9 \times 2 \times 06 + 4}$	

• **Four Digit's Numerator**

$\blacktriangleright \frac{2394}{107856} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 9 + 4}{10^7 \times 856} := \frac{2^3 \times 9 + 4}{10 \times 7^{8-5} - 6}$	$\blacktriangleright \frac{2945}{108376} := \frac{2 + 9 + 4 - 5}{-1 \times 08 + 376} := \frac{2 \times (9 - 4) - 5}{10 - (8 - 37) \times 6}$
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$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{3249}{106875} &:= \frac{32-4-9}{10 \times (6+8 \times 7) + 5} := \frac{3 \times (2+4 \times 9)}{10 \times (68+7) \times 5} & \blacktriangleright \frac{6489}{107532} &:= \frac{(6-4) \times 8-9}{-1 \times 07+5^3-2} := \frac{6-4+89}{(1+0753) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{3456}{109728} &:= \frac{3+4-5+6}{-1 \times 09+7+2^8} := \frac{34-5 \times 6}{10+9 \times (7-2+8)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{6795}{103284} &:= \frac{(6+7-9) \times 5}{10 \times 3 \times (2+8) + 4} := \frac{(6-7+9) \times 5}{(10+3^2) \times 8 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{3586}{104972} &:= \frac{3+5+8+6}{-1 \times 04+9 \times 72} := \frac{3 \times (5+8)-6}{(10 \times 49-7) \times 2} & \blacktriangleright \frac{7293}{105468} &:= \frac{7 \times 2+9+3}{(1^{05}+46) \times 8} := \frac{7+29+3}{10+546+8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{3780}{125496} &:= \frac{3 \times (7+8)+0}{(12 \times 5 \times 4+9) \times 6} := \frac{3+7+80}{(12+54 \times 9) \times 6} & \blacktriangleright \frac{7584}{120396} &:= \frac{7+5-8+4}{1-20 \times (3-9) + 6} := \frac{7+5+8-4}{1 \times 20+39 \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{3864}{109572} &:= \frac{38-6 \times 4}{1-09 \times (5-7^2)} := \frac{38-6-4}{10+((9-5) \times 7^2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{7952}{108346} &:= \frac{7-9+5 \times 2}{108+3+4-6} := \frac{(7+9) \times (5-2)}{1 \times 08 \times 3^4+6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{3928}{106547} &:= \frac{(3+9) \times 2-8}{(1+065-4) \times 7} := \frac{(3+9) \times 2+8}{(1+06 \times 5) \times 4 \times 7} & \blacktriangleright \frac{7968}{123504} &:= \frac{7+9-6-8}{1+2 \times 3 \times 5-0 \times 4} := \frac{(7-9) \times (6-8)}{1 \times 2+3 \times 5 \times 04} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4356}{120879} &:= \frac{4-3+5+6}{(1-20+8 \times 7) \times 9} := \frac{(4-3+5) \times 6}{120+879} & \blacktriangleright \frac{8253}{109647} &:= \frac{8-2+5 \times 3}{1 \times 09 \times (6 \times 4+7)} := \frac{8^2-5 \times 3}{(1+096-4) \times 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4698}{107532} &:= \frac{4+6-9+8}{10+(7 \times (5-3))^2} := \frac{46-9+8}{10 \times ((7 \times (5 \times 3))-2)} & \blacktriangleright \frac{9234}{106875} &:= \frac{9 \times (2+34)}{10 \times (68+7) \times 5} := \frac{9 \times 2 \times 3^4}{1 \times 068+7^5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5376}{109824} &:= \frac{5 \times 3-7+6}{1+(09+8)^2-4} := \frac{5 \times 3+7+6}{1 \times 09 \times 8^2-4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{9305}{124687} &:= \frac{(9-3) \times 05}{1+(2+4) \times 68-7} := \frac{930+5}{1+24 \times 6 \times 87} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5439}{120768} &:= \frac{5^4+3+9}{(1+207) \times 68} := \frac{5+43 \times 9}{1 \times 2^{07} \times 68} & \blacktriangleright \frac{9352}{104876} &:= \frac{(9-3) \times 5-2}{10-(4-8) \times 76} := \frac{(9+3-5) \times 2}{1+(04+8) \times (7+6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5629}{107384} &:= \frac{(5+6) \times 2-9}{10+7 \times (38-4)} := \frac{5 \times (6-2+9)}{10 \times (7+3 \times 8) \times 4} & \blacktriangleright \frac{9576}{123804} &:= \frac{9+5 \times (7-6)}{1+23 \times 8-04} := \frac{9+5+7 \times 6}{(1+2^3) \times 80+4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6370}{125489} &:= \frac{6-3+7+0}{1+2 \times (5+4+89)} := \frac{6 \times (3+7)+0}{1254-8 \times 9} & & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6384}{105792} &:= \frac{6-3+8-4}{1 \times (-05+7 \times 9) \times 2} := \frac{6 \times (3+8)+4}{(1+0579) \times 2} & &
 \end{aligned}$$

3.2 3 Equivalent Blocks

• Five Digit's Numerator

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10527}{49368} &:= \frac{(1+05)^2-7}{4 \times (9-3) \times 6-8} := \frac{10+5 \times 27}{(4+9 \times (3+6)) \times 8} := \frac{(10+5)^2+7}{(4+9+3) \times 68} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10598}{23467} &:= \frac{10+5-9+8}{(2^3-4) \times 6+7} := \frac{10-(5-9) \times 8}{2+(3+4+6) \times 7} := \frac{(1 \times 05+9) \times 8}{2^3 \times (4 \times 6+7)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10647}{25389} &:= \frac{10+6+4-7}{2 \times 5 \times 3-8+9} := \frac{106+4+7}{(2+5+3 \times 8) \times 9} := \frac{(1+064) \times 7}{2 \times 538+9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10692}{45738} &:= \frac{1+06+9+2}{4+5 \times 7+38} := \frac{1+069+2}{4+(5 \times 7+3) \times 8} := \frac{1 \times 06 \times 9 \times 2}{457-3+8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10725}{39468} &:= \frac{-1 \times 07+2^5}{3+9+(4+6) \times 8} := \frac{(1+07 \times 2) \times 5}{3 \times (94+6-8)} := \frac{(10+7) \times 25}{(3 \times 9-4) \times 68}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10854}{72963} &:= \frac{1+08+5+4}{7+2 \times (9 \times 6+3)} := \frac{108 \times (5-4)}{729-6+3} := \frac{1 \times 08 \times 5-4}{7 \times (29+6)-3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10863}{47925} &:= \frac{1 \times 08+6+3}{(4-7+9 \times 2) \times 5} := \frac{10+8 \times (6-3)}{(4-7+9) \times 25} := \frac{1 \times 08 \times 6+3}{(4-79) \times (2-5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10863}{59427} &:= \frac{1 \times 08+6+3}{5+9^{4-2}+7} := \frac{10+8 \times (6-3)}{5+94 \times 2-7} := \frac{(108-6) \times 3}{(5+9 \times 4)^2-7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10934}{78526} &:= \frac{1+09-3+4}{7+8 \times (5-2+6)} := \frac{109+34}{7+85 \times 2 \times 6} := \frac{10+9 \times 3-4}{7 \times (8+5^2)+6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10935}{78246} &:= \frac{1+09+35}{7 \times ((8+2) \times 4+6)} := \frac{10 \times 9 \times (3+5)}{7 \times 8 \times 2 \times 46} := \frac{1 \times 09 \times 35}{7 \times (82 \times 4-6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10962}{74385} &:= \frac{1+09+6-2}{((7-4)^3-8) \times 5} := \frac{1 \times 09 \times 6+2}{(7 \times 4 \times 3-8) \times 5} := \frac{(10+9) \times 6-2}{(7+4 \times 3) \times 8 \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12096}{35784} &:= \frac{(1+2+09) \times 6}{3 \times (5 \times (7+8)-4)} := \frac{1^2 \times 096}{3 \times (5+7) \times 8-4} := \frac{(1+2) \times 096}{3 \times (5 \times 7 \times 8+4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12495}{67830} &:= \frac{1-2 \times (4-9-5)}{6+78+30} := \frac{1 \times (2+4) \times (9+5)}{6+(7+8) \times 30} := \frac{1-(2-4) \times 9 \times 5}{(6+7) \times (8+30)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12780}{45369} &:= \frac{(12-7) \times 8+0}{4+(5-3) \times 69} := \frac{1 \times 2+78+0}{4 \times (5-3+69)} := \frac{1+27-8+0}{4-5+3+69} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12789}{63504} &:= \frac{1+27-8+9}{6+3 \times (50-4)} := \frac{1 \times 2^7+8+9}{6^3+504} := \frac{(1+2) \times (78+9)}{6^{3+5-04}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12798}{60435} &:= \frac{1 \times 2-(7-9) \times 8}{(60-43) \times 5} := \frac{1-2+7 \times 9-8}{60 \times 4+3 \times 5} := \frac{1-2-7+98}{60 \times (4+3)+5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12804}{36957} &:= \frac{(1+2+8) \times 04}{3 \times 6 \times 9-5 \times 7} := \frac{128+04}{369+5+7} := \frac{1280-4}{(3^6+9) \times 5-7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12845}{69730} &:= \frac{1-2-8 \times (4-5)}{6+9-7+30} := \frac{1 \times 2^{8-4}+5}{6 \times (9+7+3)+0} := \frac{1^2 \times 84 \times 5}{(69+7) \times 30} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12960}{38475} &:= \frac{1-29+60}{(3 \times (8-4)+7) \times 5} := \frac{1^2 \times 96+0}{3 \times (8+4+7) \times 5} := \frac{(1+2) \times 96+0}{3+847+5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12964}{53708} &:= \frac{1 \times 2 \times (9-6+4)}{5-3+7 \times 08} := \frac{1 \times 2+9+6 \times 4}{5 \times (3 \times 7+08)} := \frac{1-2+9 \times 6-4}{5^3+70+8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13428}{57069} &:= \frac{1+3-4+2 \times 8}{5-7 \times (0 \times 6-9)} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times (4+2 \times 8)}{5 \times (7 \times 06+9)} := \frac{(1+3^4) \times (2+8)}{5 \times (706-9)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13482}{59706} &:= \frac{1+3+4+8-2}{5+9 \times 7-06} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 8+2}{5+9+70 \times 6} := \frac{1-3 \times (4-8+2)}{5^{9-7}+06} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13485}{29760} &:= \frac{1-3 \times 4+8 \times 5}{2+9-7+60} := \frac{1-3+(4+8) \times 5}{2 \times (9-7)^6+0} := \frac{1-3+4+85}{2 \times (9+7) \times 6+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13509}{86742} &:= \frac{1-(3-5) \times 09}{(8-6)^7-4-2} := \frac{1-3+50+9}{8 \times (6 \times 7+4)-2} := \frac{(1+3) \times 50+9}{8 \times 6 \times 7 \times 4-2}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13572}{49068} &:= \frac{1 \times 3 + 5 + 7 - 2}{49 + 06 - 8} &:= \frac{1 + 3 \times 5 \times 7 - 2}{4 \times (90 + 6) - 8} &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 5 \times 72}{(4 + 90) \times (6 + 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{27594} &:= \frac{1 \times 36 - 0 \times 8}{2 + 7 \times 5 + 9 \times 4} &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 60 + 8}{2^7 + 5 + 9 + 4} &:= \frac{1 \times 3 \times 6 \times 08}{(27 + 5) \times 9 + 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{49572} &:= \frac{1^3 \times (6 + 08)}{4 \times (9 + 5) - 7 + 2} &:= \frac{1 \times 36 - 08}{(49 - 5 + 7) \times 2} &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 60 - 8}{(4 + (9 + 5) \times 7) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13760}{29584} &:= \frac{1 + 3 \times (7 + 6) + 0}{2 \times 9 \times 5 - 8 + 4} &:= \frac{(1 \times 3 + 7) \times 6 + 0}{2 + 95 + 8 \times 4} &:= \frac{(13 + 7) \times 6 + 0}{2 + (9 - 5)^{8-4}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13806}{24957} &:= \frac{13 \times (8 - 06)}{2 \times (4 - 9) + 57} &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 8 \times 06}{2 + 4 + 95 - 7} &:= \frac{13 \times (8 + 06)}{24 \times (9 + 5) - 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13806}{47259} &:= \frac{13 \times (8 - 06)}{4 \times 7 + 2 + 59} &:= \frac{(1 + 3) \times 806}{47^2 \times 5 - 9} &:= \frac{1 \times 3 \times 80 - 6}{(47 \times 2 - 5) \times 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13827}{46509} &:= \frac{1 - 3 + 8 + 27}{4 \times 6 \times 5 - 09} &:= \frac{13 + 82 - 7}{4 \times (65 + 09)} &:= \frac{138 + 27}{46 + 509} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13840}{29756} &:= \frac{1 \times 3 \times 8 - 4 + 0}{2 + 97 - 56} &:= \frac{(1 - 3 + 8) \times 40}{(2 + 9 + 75) \times 6} &:= \frac{(1^3 + 8) \times 40}{2 \times 9 + 756} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13869}{40572} &:= \frac{(1 + 3) \times 86 - 9}{4 \times 05 \times 7^2} &:= \frac{(1 + (3 + 8) \times 6) \times 9}{(40 - 5 + 7)^2} &:= \frac{1 + 3 \times 86 + 9}{(4 \times (0 \times 5 + 7))^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13902}{75468} &:= \frac{1 \times 3 + 9 + 02}{7 + 5 - 4 + 68} &:= \frac{1 \times 3 + 9^{02}}{(7 + 5 \times (4 + 6)) \times 8} &:= \frac{13 \times 9 + 02}{7 + 5^4 + 6 + 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13965}{20748} &:= \frac{(1 + 3 + 9 - 6) \times 5}{20 \times (7 - 4) - 8} &:= \frac{1 + 3 + 96 + 5}{2 \times 074 + 8} &:= \frac{1 + 39 + 6 \times 5}{(2 + 07 + 4) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14025}{98736} &:= \frac{(1 + 4 - 0 \times 2) \times 5}{(9 + 8) \times (7 + 3) + 6} &:= \frac{1 \times 40 \times 2 - 5}{(98 - 7 - 3) \times 6} &:= \frac{1 \times 4 \times 025}{98 \times 7 + 3 \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14320}{75896} &:= \frac{1 - 4 + 3 + 20}{7 - 5 + 8 + 96} &:= \frac{1 + (4 + 3)^2 + 0}{7 \times 5 \times 8 - 9 - 6} &:= \frac{(1 + 4) \times 3 \times 20}{((7 - 5)^8 + 9) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14352}{98670} &:= \frac{1 - 4 + 3^{5-2}}{9 + 86 + 70} &:= \frac{1 - 4 + 3 \times 5^2}{9 \times (8 \times 6 + 7) + 0} &:= \frac{1 \times 4 \times (3 + 5^2)}{(9 + 8 - 6) \times 70} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14580}{26973} &:= \frac{1^4 \times 5 \times 8 + 0}{2 - 6 \times (9 - 7 \times 3)} &:= \frac{1 + 4 - 5 + 80}{2 \times 69 + 7 + 3} &:= \frac{1 \times 4 \times 5 + 80}{2 - 6 + 9 \times 7 \times 3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14580}{67392} &:= \frac{1 + 4 + 5 \times 8 + 0}{67 \times 3 + 9 - 2} &:= \frac{1 + 4 + 580}{(6 + 7 + 39)^2} &:= \frac{1 + 4 + 5 \times 80}{(6 + 7) \times (3 + 9)^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14703}{68952} &:= \frac{1 + 4 \times 7 + 0 \times 3}{68 \times (9 - 5 - 2)} &:= \frac{(1 + 4 \times 7) \times 03}{68 \times (9 - 5 + 2)} &:= \frac{1 + 4 + 7^{03}}{6 \times 8 \times (9 + 5^2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14850}{32967} &:= \frac{(1 - 4 + 8) \times 50}{3 \times (2 \times 96 - 7)} &:= \frac{1^{48} \times 50}{3 \times (2 \times (9 + 6) + 7)} &:= \frac{(1^4 + 8) \times 50}{32 + 967} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14937}{85026} &:= \frac{1 + 49 - 37}{8 \times 5 \times 02 - 6} &:= \frac{1 \times 4 \times (9 - 3 + 7)}{8 + (50 - 2) \times 6} &:= \frac{1 + 4 + 93 - 7}{8^{5-02} + 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14985}{26730} &:= \frac{1+4 \times (9+8)+5}{(2+6 \times 7) \times 3+0} := \frac{1+49 \times (8-5)}{267-3+0} := \frac{1-49+85}{2+67-3+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14985}{63270} &:= \frac{(1-4+9) \times (8-5)}{6+(3-2) \times 70} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times (9+8)-5}{(6+32) \times 7+0} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 9 \times (8-5)}{6 \times (3 \times 2+70)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15028}{47396} &:= \frac{1 \times 5+0 \times 2+8}{47-3-9+6} := \frac{1 \times 50+28}{(47+3-9) \times 6} := \frac{(1 \times 50+2) \times 8}{4 \times (7^3-9-6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15048}{37962} &:= \frac{1-5+048}{3 \times (7+(9+6) \times 2)} := \frac{(15-04) \times 8}{37 \times (9-6) \times 2} := \frac{(1+50+4) \times 8}{37 \times (9+6) \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15067}{34892} &:= \frac{1+5+06+7}{3+48-9+2} := \frac{1-5+06 \times 7}{3-4+8+9^2} := \frac{15+06 \times 7}{3+48+9^2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15067}{89243} &:= \frac{1+5+0 \times 6+7}{8+9 \times 2 \times 4-3} := \frac{1 \times 50+67}{8 \times 92-43} := \frac{15 \times (06+7)}{8 \times 9 \times 2^4+3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{84672} &:= \frac{(1+5+3) \times 09}{(8+4 \times 6) \times 7 \times 2} := \frac{(1+5) \times 3^{09}}{84 \times 6^{7-2}} := \frac{(1+53) \times 09}{8 \times 4 \times 6 \times 7 \times 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15327}{89604} &:= \frac{1-5+3+27}{8 \times (9+6+04)} := \frac{1 \times 5 \times (3 \times 2+7)}{(89+6) \times 04} := \frac{(1+5) \times (32+7)}{8 \times 9+6^{04}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15479}{20863} &:= \frac{1-5-(4-7) \times 9}{2 \times (08+6)+3} := \frac{1 \times 5 \times (4+7)-9}{20+(8+6) \times 3} := \frac{1 \times 5+4 \times (7+9)}{2 \times 08 \times 6-3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15498}{62730} &:= \frac{1+5 \times 4 \times (9-8)}{62-7+30} := \frac{1+5+49+8}{6^2 \times 7+3+0} := \frac{1+5 \times 4 \times 9+8}{6 \times 2^7-3+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15732}{49680} &:= \frac{1 \times 57 \times (3-2)}{4+96+80} := \frac{1 \times 5+73-2}{(4 \times 9-6) \times 8+0} := \frac{1+5+73 \times 2}{4 \times (9+6) \times 8+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15732}{69084} &:= \frac{1+5 \times (7-3)+2}{69+08 \times 4} := \frac{(1+5) \times (7^3+2)}{6+9084} := \frac{(1-5+73) \times 2}{690-84} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15732}{96048} &:= \frac{1 \times 5+73-2}{(9 \times 6+04) \times 8} := \frac{1+5+73 \times 2}{960-4 \times 8} := \frac{1 \times 57 \times 3 \times 2}{9 \times (60 \times 4-8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{15790}{26843} &:= \frac{1^{57}+9+0}{2+6+8+4-3} := \frac{1 \times 5 \times (7+9)+0}{2 \times 68 \times (4-3)} := \frac{15 \times (7+9)+0}{(26+8) \times 4 \times 3} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16074}{53298} &:= \frac{1+6 \times (07-4)}{53+2 \times 9-8} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 07-4}{5^3+2-9+8} := \frac{1 \times 60-7+4}{5+(32-9) \times 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16350}{98427} &:= \frac{1^{63} \times 50}{(9-8+42) \times 7} := \frac{1+6+3^5+0}{9 \times 84 \times 2-7} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 3 \times 50}{9 \times (84+2) \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16359}{20748} &:= \frac{(1+6+3) \times 5-9}{20 \times (7-4)-8} := \frac{1-(6-3 \times 5) \times 9}{(2+07+4) \times 8} := \frac{1+63+59}{2 \times 074+8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16375}{24890} &:= \frac{(1-6+3+7) \times 5}{2-(4-8) \times 9+0} := \frac{1 \times 63+7+5}{2 \times (48+9)+0} := \frac{1-6+3 \times 7 \times 5}{2 \times (4+8 \times 9)+0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{16478}{50932} &:= \frac{1 \times 6+4-7+8}{(5+09+3) \times 2} := \frac{(1 \times 6-4) \times 7+8}{50+9+3^2} := \frac{(1+6+4) \times (7+8)}{509+3-2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16830}{49725} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 + 8 + 30}{4 + 9 \times (7 + 2 + 5)} := \frac{(1 - 6) \times (8 - 30)}{(4 + 9 \times 7 - 2) \times 5} := \frac{168 + 30}{(4 + 9) \times (7 + 2) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16974}{25830} &:= \frac{1 + 6 + (9 - 7)^4}{2 - 5 + 8 + 30} := \frac{1 + (6 + 9) \times (7 - 4)}{2^5 + 8 + 30} := \frac{(1 + 6 + 9 + 7) \times 4}{2 \times (5 \times 8 + 30)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16975}{38024} &:= \frac{1 - 6 + (9 + 7) \times 5}{3 \times (80 - 24)} := \frac{(1 \times 6 + 9) \times 7 - 5}{3 \times 80 - 2^4} := \frac{1^6 \times 9 \times 75}{(380 - 2) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16982}{70354} &:= \frac{1 - 6 + 9 + 8 + 2}{7 - 03 + 54} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 9 + 8 - 2}{70 - 3 + 5 \times 4} := \frac{1^6 - 9 + 8^2}{70 + 3 \times 54} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17289}{63054} &:= \frac{17^2 \times (8 + 9)}{63 - 05 + 4} := \frac{1 + 7^2 - 8 + 9}{6 \times (30 + 5 - 4)} := \frac{1 - 7 \times (2 - 8) - 9}{(6 + 30 - 5) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17458}{96320} &:= \frac{17 - 4 \times (5 - 8)}{9 \times 6 \times 3 - 2 + 0} := \frac{(1 \times 7 - 4) \times 58}{(9 - 6) \times 320} := \frac{1 \times 74 + 5 + 8}{96 \times (3 + 2) + 0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17543}{92680} &:= \frac{1 - 7 - 5 + 4^3}{(9 + 26) \times 8 + 0} := \frac{1 + 7 + 5^4 + 3}{(9 - 2) \times 6 \times 80} := \frac{1 + 75 \times 4 \times 3}{(9 - 2) \times 680} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17640}{53928} &:= \frac{1^7 - 6 + 40}{5 \times 3 \times 9 - 28} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times (6 + 4) + 0}{5^3 + 9^2 + 8} := \frac{(1^7 + 6) \times 40}{(5^3 - 9 \times 2) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17680}{53924} &:= \frac{(1 + 7) \times 6 - 8 + 0}{5^3 - 9 + 2 + 4} := \frac{(1 + 7 - 6) \times 80}{(5 - 3)^9 - 24} := \frac{1 - 7 + 6 + 80}{5 + 3 \times 9^2 - 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17853}{64920} &:= \frac{17 - 8 + 5 - 3}{6 + 4 \times 9 - 2 + 0} := \frac{17 + 85 - 3}{(6 - 4) \times 9 \times 20} := \frac{178 + 53}{(6 + 4 \times 9) \times 20} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17856}{94302} &:= \frac{1 + 7 \times (8 - 5 + 6)}{9 \times 4 + 302} := \frac{(1 + 7 + 8 \times 5) \times 6}{((9 + 4) \times 3)^{02}} := \frac{(1 + 7) \times (8 + 56)}{(9 + 43)^{02}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18239}{67405} &:= \frac{1 + 8 + 2 + 3 + 9}{(6 + 7 + 4) \times 05} := \frac{1 + 8 - 2 + 39}{(6 + 7 \times 4) \times 05} := \frac{1 + 8^2 + 3 \times 9}{(-6 + 74) \times 05} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18275}{40936} &:= \frac{(1 + 8 \times 2 - 7) \times 5}{40 + (9 + 3) \times 6} := \frac{1^{82} \times 75}{(40 - 9 - 3) \times 6} := \frac{(1 \times 82 - 7) \times 5}{40 \times (9 \times 3 - 6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18326}{40579} &:= \frac{(1 \times 8 + 3) \times 2 + 6}{4 - 05 + 7 \times 9} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times (3 - 2 + 6)}{40 + 5 + 79} := \frac{18 \times (3 - 2 + 6)}{40 \times 5 + 79} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18450}{37269} &:= \frac{1 \times 8 \times 450}{3 + 7269} := \frac{(18 + 4) \times 50}{3^7 + 26 + 9} := \frac{1^8 \times 450}{3 \times (7^2 \times 6 + 9)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18462}{59730} &:= \frac{1 + 8 + 4 + 6 - 2}{5^{9-7} + 30} := \frac{(1 - 8 \times (4 - 6)) \times 2}{5 \times (9 + 7) + 30} := \frac{1 - 8 - 4 + 62}{5 \times (9 \times 7 - 30)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18479}{20653} &:= \frac{1 + 8 \times (4 + 7 - 9)}{2 \times (06 + 5) - 3} := \frac{1 - 8 \times (4 - 7) + 9}{2 + 06^{5-3}} := \frac{(1 - 8) \times 4 + 79}{2 \times 06 \times 5 - 3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18564}{72930} &:= \frac{1 + 8 - 5 + 6 + 4}{7 + 2 \times 9 + 30} := \frac{1 \times 8 + 5 \times 6 + 4}{72 + 93 + 0} := \frac{18 + 56 - 4}{7 - 2 + 9 \times 30} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18972}{56304} &:= \frac{1 \times 8 + 9 + 7 \times 2}{5 + 6 + 3^{04}} := \frac{1 \times 8^{9-7} - 2}{5 \times (6 + 30) + 4} := \frac{(18 \times 9 - 7) \times 2}{5 \times (6 \times 30 + 4)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19038}{72645} &:= \frac{1^9 \times 038}{7+2 \times (64+5)} &:= \frac{1 \times 9 \times 038}{7 \times 2 + 6^4 - 5} &:= \frac{(1+9) \times 038}{(7^2 \times 6 - 4) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19278}{45360} &:= \frac{1 \times 9 - 2 + 78}{4 \times 5 + 3 \times 60} &:= \frac{1 \times 9 \times (2+7+8)}{4 \times 5 \times 3 \times 6 + 0} &:= \frac{1 \times 9 \times (2^7 + 8)}{(45+3) \times 60} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19278}{63504} &:= \frac{1 \times 9 \times 2 + 7 - 8}{(6+3+5) \times 04} &:= \frac{19 \times (2+7+8)}{(6^3 + 50) \times 4} &:= \frac{(19-2) \times (7+8)}{6 \times 35 \times 04} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19305}{42768} &:= \frac{(1+9+3) \times 05}{4 \times (2+7 \times 6 - 8)} &:= \frac{(-1+9 \times 3) \times 05}{4+276+8} &:= \frac{(1 \times 9 + 30) \times 5}{(4-2+7) \times 6 \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19350}{48762} &:= \frac{1+9+3 \times 5+0}{48+7+6+2} &:= \frac{1^{93} \times 50}{48+76+2} &:= \frac{(1+9-3) \times 50}{4+876+2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19364}{80752} &:= \frac{(1+9) \times (3+6) + 4}{8 \times 07 \times (5+2)} &:= \frac{19 + (3+6)^4}{80 \times 7^{5-2}} &:= \frac{1 \times 936 + 4}{80 \times 7 \times (5+2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19437}{65208} &:= \frac{(19+4) \times 3 - 7}{6^{5-2} - 08} &:= \frac{1 \times 9 + 4 \times 3 \times 7}{6 \times 52 + 0 \times 8} &:= \frac{1 \times 9 + 43 \times 7}{65 \times 2 \times 08} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19470}{36285} &:= \frac{19-4+7+0}{3 \times (6-2+8) + 5} &:= \frac{1-9+4+70}{36+2+85} &:= \frac{(1+9) \times (4+7) + 0}{3 \times (62+8) - 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19530}{26784} &:= \frac{1+9-5+30}{2-6+7 \times 8-4} &:= \frac{1 \times 9 \times (5+30)}{2 \times 6^{7-8+4}} &:= \frac{(1+9) \times (5+30)}{(2+6+7) \times 8 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19602}{83754} &:= \frac{19-6-02}{8-3 \times (7-5 \times 4)} &:= \frac{1+9+6 \times 02}{(8+3+7) \times 5+4} &:= \frac{196+02}{837+5+4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19647}{53280} &:= \frac{1 \times 9 + 6 \times 4 \times 7}{(5+3-2) \times 80} &:= \frac{(1+9 \times 6+4) \times 7}{(5+3^2) \times 80} &:= \frac{(19 \times 6+4) \times 7}{(5+3) \times 280} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19734}{65208} &:= \frac{1-9+73+4}{(6+5) \times 20+8} &:= \frac{(19+7-3) \times 4}{6 \times 52 - 08} &:= \frac{1-9 \times (7-3 \times 4)}{(-6+5^2) \times 08} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19836}{54720} &:= \frac{1-9+(8+3) \times 6}{(5-4+7) \times 20} &:= \frac{1+9+83-6}{5 \times (4 \times 7+20)} &:= \frac{1 \times 98+3 \times 6}{(5+4+7) \times 20} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19836}{57420} &:= \frac{1 \times 9 - 8 + 3 \times 6}{57-4+2+0} &:= \frac{1+9-8+36}{5 \times (7+4) \times 2+0} &:= \frac{19 \times (8-3+6)}{5 \times (7+4)^2 + 0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19845}{26730} &:= \frac{1 \times 9 + 84 + 5}{(2+6 \times 7) \times 3+0} &:= \frac{(19-8) \times 4+5}{2+67-3+0} &:= \frac{1+984-5}{(2+6 \times 7) \times 30} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19845}{62370} &:= \frac{1+(9-8)^4+5}{6+23-7+0} &:= \frac{1 \times 9 - 8 + 4 \times 5}{62-3+7+0} &:= \frac{1+98+4 \times 5}{6-2+370} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19872}{34560} &:= \frac{1-9+8 \times 7-2}{3^4+5-6+0} &:= \frac{198+7+2}{3 \times 4 \times 5 \times 6+0} &:= \frac{1+9 \times (8+7)+2}{(3-4+5) \times 60} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20178}{93456} &:= \frac{20+1 \times 7-8}{(9+3-4) \times (5+6)} &:= \frac{2-01+7 \times 8}{(9+(3+4) \times 5) \times 6} &:= \frac{2 \times (01+7 \times 8)}{(9+3) \times 4 \times (5+6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20196}{57834} &:= \frac{2 \times (-01+9)+6}{5 \times (7+8) - 3 \times 4} &:= \frac{2 \times (01+9 \times 6)}{5 \times 7 \times (8-3+4)} &:= \frac{(2+01 \times 9) \times 6}{(5 \times 7 - 8) \times (3+4)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{20356}{97418} &:= \frac{2 - (03 - 5) \times 6}{9 \times 7 + 4 \times 1^8} &:= \frac{2 \times (0 \times 3 + 56)}{(9 \times 7 + 4 \times 1) \times 8} &:= \frac{20 \times (3 + 5) - 6}{9^{7-4} \times 1 + 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{20358}{46197} &:= \frac{2 \times (0 \times 3 + 5 + 8)}{4 - 6 \times (1 - 9) + 7} &:= \frac{2^{03} \times (5 + 8)}{4 \times (61 - 9 + 7)} &:= \frac{2 \times 03^5 + 8}{4^{6-1} + 97} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{20394}{65817} &:= \frac{2 \times (0 \times 3 + 9) + 4}{6 \times (5 + 8 \times 1) - 7} &:= \frac{2 + 03 \times 9 \times 4}{6 \times 58 \times 1 + 7} &:= \frac{20 + 39 \times 4}{6 - 5 + 81 \times 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{20398}{45167} &:= \frac{2 \times (-03 + 9 + 8)}{4 \times 5 \times 1 + 6 \times 7} &:= \frac{2^{-03+9} - 8}{4 \times ((5 - 1) \times 6 + 7)} &:= \frac{2 + (03 + 9) \times 8}{4 \times 51 + 6 + 7} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{20736}{91584} &:= \frac{2 + 07 - 3 + 6}{9 + 1 \times 5 \times 8 + 4} &:= \frac{2 \times (07 - 3) \times 6}{(9 \times 1 \times 5 + 8) \times 4} &:= \frac{(20 - 7 - 3) \times 6}{9 + (1 - 5 + 8)^4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{20958}{64371} &:= \frac{2 + 09 - 5 + 8}{6 + 43 - 7 + 1} &:= \frac{2 \times (-09 + 58)}{6 \times (43 + 7) + 1} &:= \frac{20 \times 9 + 58}{6 - 4 + 3^{7-1}} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{21360}{94785} &:= \frac{2 \times (1 + 3) \times 6 + 0}{9 + 4 \times (7 \times 8 - 5)} &:= \frac{2 - 1 + 3 + 60}{9 + (47 + 8) \times 5} &:= \frac{2^{1+3} \times 6 + 0}{9 \times 47 + 8 - 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{21375}{64980} &:= \frac{2 \times 1^3 \times 75}{6 \times (4 + 9 \times 8) + 0} &:= \frac{2 \times (1 - 3 + 7) \times 5}{(6 + 4 + 9) \times 8 + 0} &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 3 \times 75}{6^4 + 9 \times 8 + 0} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{21450}{78936} &:= \frac{(2 - 1 + 4) \times 5 + 0}{7 \times (8 + 9 - 3) - 6} &:= \frac{(2 + 1^4) \times 50}{(7 - 8 + 93) \times 6} &:= \frac{(2 - 1) \times 4 \times 50}{7 - (8 - 9) \times 3^6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{21546}{83790} &:= \frac{2 + 1 + 54 + 6}{8 + 3 \times 79 + 0} &:= \frac{21 + 54 + 6}{(8 - 3) \times 7 \times 9 + 0} &:= \frac{(2 + 1) \times (5 + 46)}{8^3 - 7 + 90} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{21604}{57938} &:= \frac{2 \times (1 + 6 + 04)}{5 + 7 + 9 + 38} &:= \frac{2^{1+6} + 04}{5 + 7 + 9 \times 38} &:= \frac{216 + 04}{579 + 3 + 8} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{21749}{83650} &:= \frac{2 + 1 \times 7 \times 4 + 9}{(8 - 3) \times 6 \times 5 + 0} &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 7 \times 4 + 9}{(8 + 3 - 6) \times 50} &:= \frac{2 \times (17 - 4) \times 9}{(8 \times 3 - 6) \times 50} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{21780}{93654} &:= \frac{21 + 7 - 8 + 0}{(9 + 3 + 6) \times 5 - 4} &:= \frac{2 + 1 \times 78 + 0}{9 \times 36 + 5 \times 4} &:= \frac{2 + 178 + 0}{9 \times (3 \times 6 \times 5 - 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{21870}{53946} &:= \frac{(2 - 1) \times (8 + 7) + 0}{5^3 - 94 + 6} &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times (8 + 7) + 0}{5 \times (3 + 9 + 4) - 6} &:= \frac{(2 + 1) \times (8 + 7) + 0}{5 \times 3 \times 9 - 4 \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{23056}{41789} &:= \frac{2^{3-05+6}}{4 + 1 + 7 + 8 + 9} &:= \frac{2^{3+0 \times 5} \times 6}{4 + 1 - 7 + 89} &:= \frac{2^3 \times 05 \times 6}{(4 + 1) \times (78 + 9)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{23075}{84916} &:= \frac{2 \times (3 + 07) + 5}{8 + (4 + 9 + 1) \times 6} &:= \frac{2 \times (3 + 07) \times 5}{8 \times (4 \times (9 + 1) + 6)} &:= \frac{(23 + 07) \times 5}{(84 + 9 - 1) \times 6} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{23085}{49761} &:= \frac{2 + 3 + 08 \times 5}{4^{9-7} \times 6 + 1} &:= \frac{2 \times 30 \times (8 - 5)}{4 \times ((9 + 7) \times 6 + 1)} &:= \frac{2 + 308 + 5}{4 + 9 \times (76 - 1)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{23160}{89745} &:= \frac{2^{3+1^6} + 0}{8 + 9 \times (7 + 4 - 5)} &:= \frac{2 \times (3 + 1 + 60)}{8 \times (9 \times 7 + 4 - 5)} &:= \frac{2 \times 3 \times 160}{8 \times (97 - 4) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{23175}{96408} &:= \frac{2 \times (3 + 17 + 5)}{9 \times 6 \times 4 - 08} &:= \frac{(2 - 3 \times (1 - 7)) \times 5}{96 + 40 \times 8} &:= \frac{(2 + 31) \times 75}{(-9 + 6^4) \times 08} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23460}{78591} &:= \frac{2 \times (3+4) + 6+0}{(7+8) \times 5 - 9+1} &:= \frac{2+3 \times 46+0}{7 \times (8+59 \times 1)} &:= \frac{(2-3+4) \times 60}{7 \times 85+9-1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23640}{57918} &:= \frac{(2-3+6) \times 4+0}{57-9+1^8} &:= \frac{2 \times 3 \times 6+4+0}{5 \times (7+9)+18} &:= \frac{236+4+0}{579+1+8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23976}{51840} &:= \frac{2+3+9 \times 7+6}{5 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4+0} &:= \frac{2^3+97+6}{5 \times 1 \times (8+40)} &:= \frac{2 \times (3+9)+7+6}{5 \times 1 \times 8+40} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{24087}{69153} &:= \frac{2+4 \times (08+7)}{6 \times 9-1+5^3} &:= \frac{2+4+087}{6 \times 9 \times 1 \times 5-3} &:= \frac{2 \times (4+08)+7}{6+91-5-3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{24168}{39750} &:= \frac{24+16 \times 8}{(3+9-7) \times 50} &:= \frac{(2 \times 41-6) \times 8}{(3 \times 9-7) \times 50} &:= \frac{(2^{4+1}+6) \times 8}{(3+97) \times 5+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{24173}{60958} &:= \frac{2 \times (4-1+7)+3}{6 \times 0 \times 9+58} &:= \frac{2 \times 41+7+3}{60 \times (9-5)-8} &:= \frac{(24-1) \times (7+3)}{60 \times 9+5 \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{24687}{93051} &:= \frac{2 \times (4-6)+8 \times 7}{(9+30) \times 5+1} &:= \frac{2+4 \times 6 \times (8-7)}{93+05 \times 1} &:= \frac{2 \times (4+6 \times 8) \times 7}{9 \times 305-1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{24718}{93056} &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 7+1+8}{(9 \times 3+05) \times 6} &:= \frac{2+4+71+8}{9+305+6} &:= \frac{247+1 \times 8}{930+5 \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{24759}{61308} &:= \frac{2 \times (4-7+5 \times 9)}{6^{1 \times 3}-08} &:= \frac{(2^4+7+5) \times 9}{6 \times 13 \times 08} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 \times 7 \times 5 \times 9}{6 \times 130 \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25130}{97648} &:= \frac{2^{5 \times 1}+3+0}{(9-7) \times 64+8} &:= \frac{2 \times (5+1 \times 30)}{9+7+(6-4)^8} &:= \frac{2 \times 5+130}{((9-7)^6+4) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25317}{68094} &:= \frac{2+5 \times (3+1)+7}{6 \times (8+09-4)} &:= \frac{2+5+3 \times 17}{(6 \times 8-09) \times 4} &:= \frac{(2^5-3) \times (1+7)}{6 \times 8 \times (09+4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25317}{69840} &:= \frac{2+5 \times (3+1)+7}{(6+9) \times 8-40} &:= \frac{2+5+3 \times 17}{(6+9) \times 8+40} &:= \frac{253+1+7}{(6+9) \times (8+40)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25704}{39168} &:= \frac{2^5-7-04}{3 \times (9-1^6)+8} &:= \frac{2-5+70-4}{(3+9 \times 1^6) \times 8} &:= \frac{(2+5) \times (70-4)}{(3+91-6) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25714}{60398} &:= \frac{25 \times 7+1-4}{6+0398} &:= \frac{257+1^4}{6 \times (03+98)} &:= \frac{2^5+7+1 \times 4}{6-03+98} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25839}{61074} &:= \frac{2-5 \times (8-3-9)}{6 \times (1+07)+4} &:= \frac{2+58-3 \times 9}{6 \times (10+7-4)} &:= \frac{25+8 \times (3+9)}{6+10 \times 7 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{26730}{49815} &:= \frac{26-7+3+0}{49-8 \times 1^5} &:= \frac{267-3+0}{498-1-5} &:= \frac{(2+6 \times 7) \times 3+0}{(49-8) \times (1+5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{26793}{84501} &:= \frac{2+(6-7+9) \times 3}{8 \times 4+50 \times 1} &:= \frac{(2+6) \times 7 \times 9+3}{8 \times 4 \times 50-1} &:= \frac{26 \times (7+93)}{8 \times (4^5+01)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{27094}{36518} &:= \frac{27+0 \times 9-4}{3+6 \times (5+1)-8} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 09-4}{3 \times (6 \times 5+1^8)} &:= \frac{2 \times 70-94}{(3+6) \times (5+1)+8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{27160}{58394} &:= \frac{2 \times 7 \times 1+6+0}{58-3 \times (9-4)} &:= \frac{(2+7+1) \times 6+0}{5-(8-39) \times 4} &:= \frac{2 \times (7-1) \times 60}{(5 \times 8+3) \times 9 \times 4}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\blacktriangleright \frac{27360}{41895} := \frac{2 \times (7+3+6)+0}{4+(18-9) \times 5} := \frac{2 \times (7-3+60)}{(41+8) \times (9-5)} := \frac{(27-3) \times 60}{(41+8) \times 9 \times 5} \\
 &\blacktriangleright \frac{27360}{51984} := \frac{2^{7-3}-6+0}{5+1+9+8-4} := \frac{2 \times (7-3+6)+0}{5+1^9+8 \times 4} := \frac{2 \times (7 \times 3-6)+0}{5 \times 1 \times 9+8+4} \\
 &\blacktriangleright \frac{27390}{45816} := \frac{2 \times (7+3)+90}{4 \times (5 \times 8 \times 1+6)} := \frac{2+7 \times 39+0}{4-(5-81) \times 6} := \frac{2-7+390}{4+5 \times 8 \times 16} \\
 &\blacktriangleright \frac{27405}{86913} := \frac{(2-7+40) \times 5}{8 \times 69 \times 1+3} := \frac{(2+7+40) \times 5}{86 \times 9 \times 1+3} := \frac{(2+7) \times (40-5)}{86+913} \\
 &\blacktriangleright \frac{27405}{96831} := \frac{2-7+4 \times 05}{9+6 \times 8-3-1} := \frac{2+7 \times 4+0 \times 5}{96+8+3-1} := \frac{(-2+7+4) \times 05}{9+6 \times (8 \times 3+1)} \\
 &\blacktriangleright \frac{27495}{63180} := \frac{2-7+4+95}{6^{3 \times 1^8}+0} := \frac{(2 \times 7 \times 4-9) \times 5}{(6-3) \times 180} := \frac{(2^7+4+9) \times 5}{(6+3) \times 180} \\
 &\blacktriangleright \frac{27594}{38106} := \frac{2-7-5+94}{(3+8) \times 10+6} := \frac{2+7+5 \times 9 \times 4}{3 \times (81+06)} := \frac{2-75+94}{3 \times 8-1+06} \\
 &\blacktriangleright \frac{27804}{91356} := \frac{2+7+8+04}{9+1+3+56} := \frac{2-7+8+04}{9+1 \times 3+5+6} := \frac{2 \times 7+8 \times 0 \times 4}{(9-1^3) \times 5+6} \\
 &\blacktriangleright \frac{27839}{51604} := \frac{2+78-39}{5 \times 16-04} := \frac{27+8 \times (3+9)}{(51+6) \times 04} := \frac{2+(7+8+3) \times 9}{5 \times 1 \times 60+4} \\
 &\blacktriangleright \frac{27936}{40158} := \frac{2^{(7-9+3) \times 6}}{4 \times (015+8)} := \frac{2-7+9 \times 3-6}{(4-01) \times 5+8} := \frac{2 \times (7+9) \times (3+6)}{401+5+8} \\
 &\blacktriangleright \frac{27936}{48015} := \frac{2 \times (7-9+3 \times 6)}{(4+8-01) \times 5} := \frac{2+7+93-6}{(4 \times 8+01) \times 5} := \frac{2 \times (7+9) \times (3+6)}{480+15} \\
 &\blacktriangleright \frac{28143}{50976} := \frac{2+8+1 \times 43}{5+097-6} := \frac{2 \times 8+143}{(50-9+7) \times 6} := \frac{2^8-(1-4) \times 3}{5 \times (09+7) \times 6} \\
 &\blacktriangleright \frac{28457}{36019} := \frac{2+84+57}{3 \times 60+1^9} := \frac{2+84 \times 5+7}{3+60 \times 1 \times 9} := \frac{2^8+4^5+7}{(3 \times 60+1) \times 9} \\
 &\blacktriangleright \frac{28739}{60451} := \frac{2+8+7+3+9}{6+04+51} := \frac{2+87+3 \times 9}{60 \times 4+5-1} := \frac{2+8 \times (7-3) \times 9}{604+5+1} \\
 &\blacktriangleright \frac{29053}{78614} := \frac{2 \times (9+05+3)}{7+86-1^4} := \frac{(29+05) \times 3}{7 \times 8 \times (6-1)-4} := \frac{2+9+05^3}{(7+86-1) \times 4} \\
 &\blacktriangleright \frac{29160}{74358} := \frac{2 \times (9+1^6)+0}{74-3 \times 5-8} := \frac{2 \times (9+1+60)}{7 \times (4^3-5-8)} := \frac{2 \times (9-1) \times 60}{(7 \times 43+5) \times 8} \\
 &\blacktriangleright \frac{29187}{40365} := \frac{2 \times (9+18)-7}{(4+03+6) \times 5} := \frac{(29+18) \times 7}{(4+03) \times 65} := \frac{2+91+8-7}{40+3 \times 6 \times 5} \\
 &\blacktriangleright \frac{29403}{51678} := \frac{(2+9) \times 4 \times 03}{((5+1) \times 6-7) \times 8} := \frac{(-2+9+4) \times 03}{51+6-7+8} := \frac{2-9+403}{(5 \times 16+7) \times 8} \\
 &\blacktriangleright \frac{29475}{61308} := \frac{(2 \times (9-4))^{7-5}}{6^{1 \times 3}-08} := \frac{(29-4) \times (7+5)}{6 \times 13 \times 08} := \frac{2 \times (9-4) \times 7 \times 5}{(61+30) \times 8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29637}{84105} &:= \frac{2+9+(6+3) \times 7}{(8 \times 4+10) \times 5} := \frac{2 \times (9 \times (6+3)-7)}{84 \times 1 \times 05} := \frac{(2 \times 9-6) \times 37}{84 \times (10+5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29638}{71540} &:= \frac{2+9-6+3 \times 8}{7 \times (1+5+4)+0} := \frac{2 \times (96-38)}{7 \times 1^5 \times 40} := \frac{29 \times (6-3) \times 8}{7 \times (1+5) \times 40} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29736}{58410} &:= \frac{2 \times ((9-7)^3+6)}{5 \times (8+4-1)+0} := \frac{2-9+7 \times (3+6)}{5 \times (8+4+10)} := \frac{2 \times (9 \times (7-3)+6)}{5 \times (8 \times 4+1)+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30267}{58941} &:= \frac{3 \times (-02+6)+7}{5+8 \times (9-4-1)} := \frac{30 \times (2+6)+7}{58 \times 9-41} := \frac{(30+2+6) \times 7}{58 \times 9-4 \times 1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30275}{89614} &:= \frac{3+027-5}{8+9+61-4} := \frac{30+2 \times 7 \times 5}{8 \times (9+(6+1) \times 4)} := \frac{(3+027) \times 5}{8 \times (9 \times 6+1)+4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30426}{81597} &:= \frac{30-4+2-6}{8-1+59-7} := \frac{30+4 \times 2+6}{8 \times 15-9+7} := \frac{30+4 \times 2^6}{(81+5) \times 9-7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30492}{67518} &:= \frac{3+04+9-2}{6-7+(5-1) \times 8} := \frac{3+(-04+9)^2}{67-5 \times 1^8} := \frac{(30+4) \times 9+2}{675-1+8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30825}{96174} &:= \frac{3 \times (08+2)-5}{9-6+1+74} := \frac{30 \times (8-2)-5}{9 \times 61-7+4} := \frac{3 \times (08+2) \times 5}{9 \times (6 \times (1+7)+4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31064}{57892} &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 06+4}{5+(7+8-9)^2} := \frac{3-1+064}{5 \times 7+8 \times (9+2)} := \frac{3 \times (10+6)-4}{5-7-8+92} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31206}{95847} &:= \frac{3-1+2 \times 06}{9-5-8+47} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times (20-6)}{9-5 \times 8 \times (4-7)} := \frac{31 \times 2-06}{95+84-7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31590}{62478} &:= \frac{31+59+0}{6 \times (24+7)-8} := \frac{(3+1^5) \times 90}{(6 \times 2^4-7) \times 8} := \frac{3 \times (15+90)}{624+7-8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31620}{58497} &:= \frac{3+1+6^2+0}{(5+8-4) \times 9-7} := \frac{(3+1+6)^2+0}{5 \times (8+4 \times 9-7)} := \frac{(31+6) \times 20}{(5+8 \times 4)^{9-7}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31650}{78492} &:= \frac{31-6+50}{(7 \times (8+4)+9) \times 2} := \frac{(31-6) \times 5+0}{7 \times (8+4 \times 9)+2} := \frac{(3+1^6) \times 50}{7 \times 84-92} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31752}{94608} &:= \frac{3+1-7+52}{94+60-8} := \frac{(3+17) \times 5-2}{(9-4) \times 60-8} := \frac{(3-1+7+5)^2}{(9+4+60) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31824}{90576} &:= \frac{3-1+8+2^4}{9+05 \times (7+6)} := \frac{(3+1 \times 8)^2-4}{9 \times (-05+7 \times 6)} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times (82-4)}{90+576} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31968}{47520} &:= \frac{(3-1+9) \times 6+8}{(4+7) \times 5 \times 2+0} := \frac{319+6+8}{475+20} := \frac{(3-1)^9-68}{(4 \times 7+5) \times 20} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31968}{57024} &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times (9+6)-8}{5 \times 7 \times 02-4} := \frac{(3-1+9) \times 6+8}{(5 \times 7-02) \times 4} := \frac{319+6+8}{570+24} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{32509}{41876} &:= \frac{(3-2) \times (50+9)}{4 \times (18+7-6)} := \frac{(3+2) \times (50+9)}{(4+1^8) \times 76} := \frac{32 \times (50+9)}{4 \times 1 \times 8 \times 76} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{34560}{89712} &:= \frac{(3+4+5) \times 60}{89 \times 7 \times (1+2)} := \frac{(3-4+5) \times 60}{89 \times 7 \times 1^2} := \frac{(3+45) \times 60}{89 \times 7 \times 12}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \blacktriangleright \frac{34780}{59126} := \frac{(3 \times 4 - 7) \times 8 + 0}{5 - 9 \times (1 - 2 - 6)} := \frac{34 \times 7 - 8 + 0}{5 \times 91 - 2^6} := \frac{3 \times (4 \times 7 - 8) + 0}{(5 + 9 + 1 + 2) \times 6} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{35280}{67914} := \frac{3 \times 5 \times 2 \times 8 + 0}{6 \times (7 \times 9 + 14)} := \frac{352 + 8 + 0}{679 + 14} := \frac{3 - 5 + 2 + 80}{67 + 91 - 4} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{35819}{76024} := \frac{3 + 5 + 81 + 9}{(7 + 6) \times 02^4} := \frac{3 \times (5 \times 8 \times 1 + 9)}{(7 + 6) \times 024} := \frac{3 \times (5 + 8) + 1 + 9}{(7 + 6) \times 02 \times 4} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{36108}{59472} := \frac{3 + 6 + 1 \times 08}{5 \times (9 + 4 - 7) - 2} := \frac{3 + 6 \times 1 \times 08}{(5 + 9 + 4 \times 7) \times 2} := \frac{36 - 10 + 8}{5 \times (9 + 4) - 7 - 2} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{36192}{57408} := \frac{3 - (6 - 19) \times 2}{5 - 7 + 40 + 8} := \frac{36 - 1 + 9^2}{(-5 + 7 \times 4) \times 08} := \frac{3 \times (6 \times 19 + 2)}{(-5 + 74) \times 08} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{37125}{40986} := \frac{(37 - 12) \times 5}{(40 - 9 - 8) \times 6} := \frac{3 \times (7 + (1 + 2)^5)}{(40 + 98) \times 6} := \frac{(3 \times 7 - 1)^2 \times 5}{(40 \times 9 + 8) \times 6} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{37150}{69842} := \frac{3 + 7 + 15 + 0}{6 - 9 + 8 + 42} := \frac{(3 + 7 \times 1) \times 5 + 0}{(6 + 9 + 8 \times 4) \times 2} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1 \times 50}{6 + 984 \times 2} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{37260}{94185} := \frac{3 + 7 + 26 + 0}{9 - 4 + 1 + 85} := \frac{3 + 7 + 2 + 60}{(9 + 4 + 1) \times (8 + 5)} := \frac{3 \times 72 \times 60}{(9^4 - 1 - 8) \times 5} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{37521}{64809} := \frac{3 - 7 + 5 \times (2 + 1)}{6 - 4 + 8 + 09} := \frac{3 - 7 + 5 + 21}{6 + 4 \times (8 - 0 \times 9)} := \frac{3 \times (7 + 5 \times (2 + 1))}{6 + (4 + 8) \times 09} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{37590}{46182} := \frac{3 \times 7 + 5 + 9 + 0}{46 - 1^8 - 2} := \frac{3 + 7 + 5 + 90}{4 + 61 + 8^2} := \frac{(3 - 7) \times 5 + 90}{(4 + 6 + 1) \times 8 - 2} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{37694}{85012} := \frac{(3 + 7) \times 6 - 9 - 4}{8 + (50 - 1) \times 2} := \frac{(3 - 7 + 6) \times 94}{8 \times (50 + 1 + 2)} := \frac{(3 + 7 - 6) \times 94}{850 - 1 \times 2} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{37905}{62814} := \frac{3 \times 7 + 9 + 05}{6 \times (2 + 8 - 1) + 4} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 9 \times 05}{6 \times (2^8 + 1 + 4)} := \frac{3 + 7 + 90 + 5}{6 \times (28 + 1^4)} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{37908}{64152} := \frac{3 - 7 + 9 + 08}{6 + 4 \times (1 + 5 - 2)} := \frac{3 - 7 + 90 - 8}{(6 + 4 \times 15) \times 2} := \frac{(-3 + 7 + 9) \times 08}{6 \times 4 + 152} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{38016}{45792} := \frac{38 + 01 \times 6}{4 + (5 - 7 + 9)^2} := \frac{3 + 80 - 1 + 6}{4 \times (5 \times 7 - 9) + 2} := \frac{(3 + 8) \times 016}{4 \times (5 \times 7 + 9 \times 2)} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{38640}{97152} := \frac{3 + 8 + 6 \times 4 + 0}{(9 + 7 \times 1 \times 5) \times 2} := \frac{(3 + 8) \times 6 + 4 + 0}{(9 + 7) \times (1 + 5 \times 2)} := \frac{3 \times 8 \times 6 - 4 + 0}{9 + 7^{1 \times 5 - 2}} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{38719}{62450} := \frac{38 - 7 \times 1^9}{6 - 2 - 4 + 50} := \frac{(3 + 8) \times (71 - 9)}{(6 + 2^4) \times 50} := \frac{3 \times 8 \times (71 - 9)}{6 \times 2 \times 4 \times 50} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{38916}{40572} := \frac{38 + 9 \times 1^6}{4 + 05 \times (7 + 2)} := \frac{(38 + 9) \times 16}{(4 \times (0 \times 5 + 7))^2} := \frac{3 \times 8 + 916}{4 \times 05 \times 7^2} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{39025}{87416} := \frac{3 + 90 + 2 + 5}{8 \times 7 \times 4 \times 1^6} := \frac{3 + 90 + 2^5}{8 \times 7 \times (4 + 1^6)} := \frac{(-3 + 9) \times 025}{8 \times (7 + 41 - 6)} \\ & \blacktriangleright \frac{39057}{68142} := \frac{3 + 9 + 05 \times 7}{(6 - 8) \times (1 - 42)} := \frac{39 \times 05 - 7}{6 + 81 \times 4 - 2} := \frac{3 \times 90 + 5 + 7}{6 + 81 \times (4 + 2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{39072}{54168} &:= \frac{3+90-7^2}{5+4 \times 1 \times (6+8)} &:= \frac{3+90-7+2}{54+1 \times 68} &:= \frac{(3+9 \times 07) \times 2}{5 \times (41-6)+8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{39104}{65728} &:= \frac{3+91-0 \times 4}{6 \times 5 \times (7-2)+8} &:= \frac{(3+91) \times 04}{(65+7 \times 2) \times 8} &:= \frac{3 \times 910-4}{6+572 \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{39105}{86742} &:= \frac{(3+9-1) \times 05}{(8-6)^7-4-2} &:= \frac{(3+9+10) \times 5}{(8 \times 6+74) \times 2} &:= \frac{3 \times 9 \times 10+5}{86 \times 7+4 \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{39168}{74052} &:= \frac{(3+9 \times 1) \times 6-8}{(7+4-0 \times 5)^2} &:= \frac{(3+9 \times 1) \times 6 \times 8}{(7 \times 4+05)^2} &:= \frac{(3+91-6) \times 8}{7+4)^{05-2}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{39204}{51678} &:= \frac{3 \times (92-04)}{5 \times (1+67)+8} &:= \frac{3-9+204}{5+(1-6+7)^8} &:= \frac{3 \times (9 \times 20-4)}{(5 \times 16+7) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{39410}{87265} &:= \frac{3 \times (9-4)-1+0}{8-7 \times (2-6)-5} &:= \frac{3 \times (9+4+1)+0}{8 \times (7-2+6)+5} &:= \frac{3+94+1+0}{87+2 \times 65} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{39501}{82764} &:= \frac{3 \times 9-5-01}{(8+2+7-6) \times 4} &:= \frac{3 \times (9+5 \times 01)}{8 \times (2+7+6-4)} &:= \frac{3 \times 9 \times (50-1)}{8+2764} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{39514}{68720} &:= \frac{3-9 \times 5 \times (1-4)}{6 \times 8 \times (7-2)+0} &:= \frac{3 \times (95+1-4)}{6 \times (8+72)+0} &:= \frac{3 \times 95+14}{6 \times 87-2+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{39540}{61287} &:= \frac{(3+9) \times 5-40}{6 \times (12-8)+7} &:= \frac{39+5-4+0}{6+1^2 \times 8 \times 7} &:= \frac{(3+9) \times 5 \times 40}{61^2-8+7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{39627}{51408} &:= \frac{3-9+6^2+7}{(5+1^{40}) \times 8} &:= \frac{3 \times 9 \times 6-2 \times 7}{5 \times 1 \times 40-8} &:= \frac{3+9 \times 6+2^7}{5 \times 1 \times (40+8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{39840}{61752} &:= \frac{3+9+8+40}{6+17 \times 5+2} &:= \frac{(3-9+8) \times 40}{61 \times (7-5)+2} &:= \frac{(3+9) \times 8+4+0}{6-1+75 \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{40215}{76983} &:= \frac{(40+2 \times 1) \times 5}{7 \times 6 \times 9+8 \times 3} &:= \frac{40 \times (2+1 \times 5)}{7 \times (69+8)-3} &:= \frac{40+2 \times 15}{7 \times 6+9+83} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{40352}{61789} &:= \frac{4+03+5^2}{(6-1^7) \times 8+9} &:= \frac{(40+3+5)^2}{(6+1) \times 7 \times 8 \times 9} &:= \frac{4^{(03+5) \times 2}}{(6+1) \times 7 \times 8^9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{40365}{81972} &:= \frac{(4+03+6) \times 5}{8-(1-9 \times 7) \times 2} &:= \frac{40+3 \times 6 \times 5}{8+1 \times (9+7)^2} &:= \frac{4 \times (0 \times 3+65)}{8 \times (1+9 \times 7+2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{40986}{57132} &:= \frac{40-9+8-6}{(5+(7-1) \times 3) \times 2} &:= \frac{4+09+86}{5 \times 7 \times (1+3)-2} &:= \frac{4 \times (09 \times 8-6)}{5 \times (71+3)-2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41025}{86973} &:= \frac{(4-1+02) \times 5}{(8+6) \times 9-73} &:= \frac{4 \times 10 \times 2 \times 5}{8 \times (6+97+3)} &:= \frac{4 \times 10 \times 25}{8+6 \times (9+7^3)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41268}{59730} &:= \frac{4+1 \times 26+8}{5^{9-7}+30} &:= \frac{4 \times (1+26-8)}{5 \times (9+7)+30} &:= \frac{4 \times (1+2^6-8)}{5 \times (9 \times 7+3)+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41375}{62890} &:= \frac{(4+13-7) \times 5}{6-2+8 \times 9+0} &:= \frac{4-1-3+75}{6 \times (2+8+9)+0} &:= \frac{(41-3) \times 75}{6 \times (2+8 \times 90)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41860}{79235} &:= \frac{4+18+6+0}{7+9+2+35} &:= \frac{4-1 \times 8+60}{7+9 \times (2 \times 3+5)} &:= \frac{4 \times (1+8 \times 6)+0}{7 \times (9 \times 2+35)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41895}{70623} &:= \frac{4-1+8 \times (9-5)}{7 \times (06+2)+3} := \frac{4-1+8 \times 9-5}{70+6 \times 2^3} := \frac{((4+1) \times 8+9) \times 5}{7 \times (062-3)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41952}{76038} &:= \frac{4+1 \times 9+5-2}{7 \times (6-03)+8} := \frac{4+1-9+52}{76+03+8} := \frac{4 \times (1+9 \times 5) \times 2}{7+60 \times (3+8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42350}{79618} &:= \frac{(42+3) \times 5+0}{7-(9-61) \times 8} := \frac{(4-2) \times 3 \times 50}{7+9 \times 61+8} := \frac{(4+2 \times 3) \times 5+0}{7+96-1-8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42756}{80931} &:= \frac{4+2 \times (7-5) \times 6}{80-9 \times 3 \times 1} := \frac{4 \times (27-5+6)}{(80-9) \times 3-1} := \frac{4 \times (2+(7-5) \times 6)}{80+9 \times 3-1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42806}{59173} &:= \frac{4 \times (2+8)-06}{5-9+17 \times 3} := \frac{4^2+80+6}{(5 \times (9-1)+7) \times 3} := \frac{4+2 \times 80+6}{(5+9) \times 17-3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42873}{69150} &:= \frac{4-2+8+7 \times 3}{6 \times 9+1-5+0} := \frac{(4+2+8 \times 7) \times 3}{6 \times (9+1) \times 5+0} := \frac{4^2 \times 87+3}{(6+9) \times 150} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{43168}{59072} &:= \frac{43-16-8}{(-5+9) \times 07-2} := \frac{4-3+(1+6) \times 8}{5 \times (9+07)-2} := \frac{4+3+1+68}{5+90+7+2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{45108}{69273} &:= \frac{4 \times (5+10-8)}{6 \times 9-2 \times 7+3} := \frac{4 \times (5+1+08)}{6+9-2+73} := \frac{(45-10) \times 8}{6+9^2+7^3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{45621}{73980} &:= \frac{4 \times 56-2 \times 1}{7^3+9+8+0} := \frac{4 \times (56 \times 2-1)}{(7+3) \times 9 \times 8+0} := \frac{4 \times (5+6-2)+1}{7-3 \times 9+80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{45960}{71238} &:= \frac{4+5-9+60}{71+2 \times (3+8)} := \frac{4^5+96+0}{((7-1) \times 2)^3+8} := \frac{4 \times 5 \times 9-60}{(7-1) \times (23+8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{45960}{78132} &:= \frac{45-9-6+0}{7 \times (8-1^3)+2} := \frac{4-5-9+60}{78+1+3 \times 2} := \frac{4 \times (5 \times 9+60)}{7 \times (8 \times 13-2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{46215}{70389} &:= \frac{(4+6+2+1) \times 5}{7+03+89} := \frac{4^{6-2}-1+5}{7+0389} := \frac{(46 \times 2-1) \times 5}{7 \times (03+8) \times 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{46310}{59782} &:= \frac{4 \times 6+31+0}{5-9-7+82} := \frac{4+6^3 \times 1+0}{59+(7+8)^2} := \frac{(4+6)^3-10}{5 \times (9-7)^8-2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4635}{102897} &:= \frac{(4-6+3) \times 5}{1-02 \times (8-9 \times 7)} := \frac{(4+6-3) \times 5}{10^2+8 \times 97} := \frac{4+6+35}{102+897} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{46593}{78120} &:= \frac{4 \times 65-93}{(7+8-1) \times 20} := \frac{4-65+9^3}{7 \times 8 \times 1 \times 20} := \frac{4^6+5-93}{7 \times 8 \times 120} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{47385}{91260} &:= \frac{4 \times ((7-3) \times 8-5)}{(9-1) \times 26+0} := \frac{47+3+85}{(9+1) \times 26+0} := \frac{(4+7 \times 38) \times 5}{(9+1) \times 260} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{47502}{96831} &:= \frac{(4+7 \times 5) \times 02}{9+6 \times (8 \times 3+1)} := \frac{(47+5) \times 02}{9+68 \times 3-1} := \frac{47+5-0 \times 2}{96+8+3-1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{47982}{50163} &:= \frac{4-7+9+8 \times 2}{5+01 \times 6 \times 3} := \frac{47-9+8-2}{50-1-6+3} := \frac{4+7-9+8^2}{5+01+63} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{48120}{63759} &:= \frac{4 \times (8+1 \times 2)+0}{6+3+7 \times 5+9} := \frac{(4+8 \times 1) \times 20}{6-3+7 \times 5 \times 9} := \frac{(4+8) \times 120}{6 \times (3+7 \times 5 \times 9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{48375}{61920} &:= \frac{4 \times (8+37+5)}{(6+1+9)^2+0} &:= \frac{(4 \times 8+3) \times 7+5}{(6+1+9) \times 20} &:= \frac{4 \times (8+37) \times 5}{6 \times 192+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{49058}{67132} &:= \frac{4+9 \times 05+8}{6 \times (7+1+3+2)} &:= \frac{4-9 \times (0 \times 5-8)}{(6+7) \times (1+3) \times 2} &:= \frac{4+90+58}{(6+7) \times (1+3)^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{49062}{85137} &:= \frac{4+(9+06) \times 2}{(8+5) \times (1+3)+7} &:= \frac{4 \times (9+06+2)}{8+5 \times (1+3 \times 7)} &:= \frac{4+90+6+2}{8 \times 5+137} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{49312}{85760} &:= \frac{4 \times (9-3)-1^2}{8 \times 5 \times (7-6)+0} &:= \frac{4+9+31+2}{8+5+7+60} &:= \frac{4 \times 9+31+2}{(8+5+7) \times 6+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{49368}{70125} &:= \frac{(4+9+3+6) \times 8}{7+(01+2)^5} &:= \frac{4 \times (9 \times 3 \times 6-8)}{7 \times 0125} &:= \frac{4 \times (93 \times 6-8)}{(7-01 \times 2)^5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{49725}{63180} &:= \frac{4-9+7 \times 25}{6^{3 \times 18}+0} &:= \frac{4+(9+7)^2-5}{6 \times 3 \times 18+0} &:= \frac{(4+9+72) \times 5}{(6-3) \times 180} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{49761}{52380} &:= \frac{4 \times (9 \times 7-6 \times 1)}{5 \times 2 \times 3 \times 8+0} &:= \frac{(4+9) \times 76 \times 1}{(5+2^3) \times 80} &:= \frac{49 \times 76 \times 1}{(52-3) \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{51240}{67893} &:= \frac{5 \times 1 \times 2 \times 4+0}{67-8-9+3} &:= \frac{5 \times 1 \times 24+0}{(6+7 \times 8-9) \times 3} &:= \frac{5 \times 1 \times 2 \times 40}{67 \times 8-9+3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{51408}{79632} &:= \frac{51 \times (4+08)}{79 \times (6+3 \times 2)} &:= \frac{51+408}{79+632} &:= \frac{51-4 \times 0 \times 8}{7-9+(6+3)^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{51840}{97632} &:= \frac{5 \times 1 \times (8+4)+0}{97+6 \times 3-2} &:= \frac{5 \times 1 \times (8+40)}{9+7 \times 63+2} &:= \frac{5 \times 18 \times 4+0}{9 \times 76-3 \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{52839}{74160} &:= \frac{5 \times 2+8+39}{74+1 \times 6+0} &:= \frac{(52+8) \times 3-9}{(7-4+1) \times 60} &:= \frac{(52+8-3) \times 9}{(7+4+1) \times 60} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{52904}{87136} &:= \frac{5+29-0 \times 4}{8 \times 7 \times 1^{36}} &:= \frac{5 \times (2+9)-04}{(8-7+13) \times 6} &:= \frac{(5+29) \times 04}{8 \times 7 \times (1-3+6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{52947}{80136} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 \times (9+4 \times 7)}{80 \times (13-6)} &:= \frac{5 \times (2+(9-4) \times 7)}{8 \times (-01+36)} &:= \frac{5+29-4+7}{8 \times (013-6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{53169}{80472} &:= \frac{5 \times (3+1)+6 \times 9}{8 \times (0 \times 4+7 \times 2)} &:= \frac{5 \times (3+1) \times 6-9}{(8+04) \times 7 \times 2} &:= \frac{53-1-6-9}{(8-04) \times 7 \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{53217}{84096} &:= \frac{53+21+7}{8+40 \times (9-6)} &:= \frac{5^3 \times 2 \times 1-7}{(8-4) \times 096} &:= \frac{5 \times 3^{(2-1) \times 7}}{8 \times 40 \times 9 \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{53406}{71982} &:= \frac{5+3 \times 4+06}{7-1+9+8 \times 2} &:= \frac{5+3^4+06}{7 \times (1+9+8)-2} &:= \frac{5+3+406}{7 \times (1+9) \times 8-2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{53418}{79206} &:= \frac{53-(4-1) \times 8}{7-9 \times (2-06)} &:= \frac{5^3+41+8}{(7 \times 9-20) \times 6} &:= \frac{5 \times 3^4+1^8}{7 \times (92-06)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{53460}{71928} &:= \frac{5 \times (3-4)+60}{71+9+2-8} &:= \frac{5^3 \times 4-60}{((7+1) \times 9+2) \times 8} &:= \frac{5 \times 34-60}{7 \times (1+9) \times 2+8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{53628}{71940} &:= \frac{5+3 \times (6-2+8)}{7-1+9+40} &:= \frac{53+62+8}{71+94+0} &:= \frac{5 \times (3+6) \times 2-8}{7 \times (1+9)+40}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{54270}{63918} &:= \frac{(5-4) \times 270}{6+39 \times 1 \times 8} &:= \frac{5 \times (4-2+7)+0}{6+39+1 \times 8} &:= \frac{5 \times (4-2+70)}{(63-9-1) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{56712}{93408} &:= \frac{(5+6+7-1) \times 2}{(9+3) \times 4+08} &:= \frac{5+6 \times (7-1)^2}{93 \times 4-08} &:= \frac{(56 \times 7-1) \times 2}{(9-3)^4-08} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{56943}{71820} &:= \frac{56-9+4^3}{7 \times (18+2)+0} &:= \frac{56+943}{7 \times (1+8) \times 20} &:= \frac{(5+69) \times 4 \times 3}{7 \times 1 \times 8 \times 20} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{57321}{69480} &:= \frac{5 \times (7+3 \times 2)+1}{(6-9+4) \times 80} &:= \frac{(5+7) \times (32+1)}{(6+9) \times 4 \times 8+0} &:= \frac{573+21}{(6+9) \times 48+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{59048}{61732} &:= \frac{5+9+0 \times 4+8}{6+1+7+3^2} &:= \frac{5-9+048}{6+1+7+32} &:= \frac{5 \times (9 \times 04+8)}{6+1 \times 7 \times 32} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{59064}{87312} &:= \frac{5+9 \times (06-4)}{8-7+31+2} &:= \frac{5 \times 9+06 \times 4}{87+3+12} &:= \frac{5 \times (90+6-4)}{8 \times (73+12)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{59148}{76320} &:= \frac{5+9+1 \times 48}{(7-6+3) \times 20} &:= \frac{5 \times (9+14+8)}{(7+6-3) \times 20} &:= \frac{(59+1) \times 4+8}{(7+6+3) \times 20} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{60324}{91857} &:= \frac{(6+03+2) \times 4}{9+1^8+57} &:= \frac{60+3 \times 24}{9+185+7} &:= \frac{60+32-4}{91+8+5 \times 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{61047}{82593} &:= \frac{6+1 \times 04+7}{8-2+5+9+3} &:= \frac{6+1 \times 04 \times 7}{8+2^5+9-3} &:= \frac{61-0 \times 4+7}{8+2 \times (5+9) \times 3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{62310}{97485} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 \times 310}{97 \times (4+8) \times 5} &:= \frac{62 \times 3 \times 1+0}{(9+7 \times 4) \times 8-5} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 \times 31+0}{97+485} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{62814}{70395} &:= \frac{6 \times (2+8-1)+4}{(7-03+9) \times 5} &:= \frac{6-2+8 \times 14}{70+(3+9) \times 5} &:= \frac{6 \times 281-4}{70 \times 3 \times 9-5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{63495}{82170} &:= \frac{6+3+4+9-5}{8+2 \times 1 \times 7+0} &:= \frac{6-3+(4+9) \times 5}{82-1+7+0} &:= \frac{6 \times (3 \times (4+9)-5)}{8+2^{1+7}+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{64512}{79380} &:= \frac{6 \times 4 \times 512}{7 \times 9 \times 3 \times 80} &:= \frac{64 \times (5+1) \times 2}{7+938+0} &:= \frac{(6 \times 4)^{5-1^2}}{7 \times 9^3 \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{64752}{93081} &:= \frac{64-7-5^2}{9+30+8-1} &:= \frac{(6+4-7+5)^2}{93+0 \times 8-1} &:= \frac{(6 \times (4-7+5))^2}{9 \times (3 \times 08-1)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{64870}{92315} &:= \frac{6-(4-8) \times 70}{92+315} &:= \frac{6 \times (4 \times 8+7)+0}{9 \times 2+315} &:= \frac{(6-4) \times (8+70)}{9 \times 23+15} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{65128}{70943} &:= \frac{6+5 \times 1 \times (2+8)}{(7+09) \times 4-3} &:= \frac{(6+5+1+2) \times 8}{70+9+43} &:= \frac{6 \times (5-1) \times 28}{(70-9) \times 4 \times 3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{65314}{90287} &:= \frac{6+(5+3-1) \times 4}{9 \times (-02+8)-7} &:= \frac{65+3 \times 1^4}{9-02+87} &:= \frac{(65+3) \times 14}{(90 \times 2+8) \times 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{67053}{82194} &:= \frac{6+7 \times (05+3)}{8-(2-19) \times 4} &:= \frac{6-7+05^3}{(8+21+9) \times 4} &:= \frac{6 \times (70-5-3)}{8 \times (21+9 \times 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{68103}{94752} &:= \frac{6 \times 8+1-03}{9-4+7+52} &:= \frac{68+1^{03}}{(9+4+7 \times 5) \times 2} &:= \frac{(68+1) \times 03}{9 \times 4^{7-5} \times 2}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{68241}{79350} &:= \frac{6 \times 8 \times (2+41)}{(7+9) \times 3 \times 50} &:= \frac{68-24-1}{7+93-50} &:= \frac{6+82+41}{7+93+50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{68450}{91723} &:= \frac{(6-8+4) \times 50}{9+(1 \times 7-2)^3} &:= \frac{(6+8-4) \times 5+0}{(9-1^7)^2+3} &:= \frac{(6+84) \times 5+0}{9 \times ((1+7)^2+3)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{69012}{73485} &:= \frac{6 \times 9 \times 01 \times 2}{7-3 \times (4-8 \times 5)} &:= \frac{6 \times 90 \times 12}{(7^3 \times 4+8) \times 5} &:= \frac{6 \times 90 \times 1 \times 2}{(7 \times 34-8) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{69148}{73250} &:= \frac{6+(9+1+4) \times 8}{73+2+50} &:= \frac{6 \times (91-4 \times 8)}{(73+2) \times 5+0} &:= \frac{(6 \times 9+1+4) \times 8}{(7+3)^2 \times 5+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{69153}{87024} &:= \frac{6+91-5-3}{8 \times 7 \times (-02+4)} &:= \frac{6 \times 9-1+5^3}{8 \times 7 \times (0 \times 2+4)} &:= \frac{6 \times 9 \times 1 \times 5-3}{8 \times 7 \times (02+4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{69325}{80417} &:= \frac{6-9+3+25}{8+04+17} &:= \frac{6 \times 9 \times (3+2)+5}{80 \times 4-1^7} &:= \frac{693+2+5}{804+1+7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{69483}{72105} &:= \frac{6-9 \times 4+83}{7-2+10 \times 5} &:= \frac{(6+9) \times 4 \times 8-3}{7^2 \times 10+5} &:= \frac{694-8+3}{72 \times 10-5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{69510}{73482} &:= \frac{6+9+510}{73+482} &:= \frac{6 \times (9 \times 5-10)}{7 \times 34-8 \times 2} &:= \frac{6 \times 9 \times 5+10}{7 \times (34+8)+2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{70649}{85312} &:= \frac{7 \times 06 \times 4-9}{8 \times (5-3) \times 12} &:= \frac{70 \times 6-49}{8 \times (53+1+2)} &:= \frac{(70-6) \times 4+9}{8 \times 5 \times (3+1) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{71540}{98623} &:= \frac{7 \times 1 \times 5 \times 4+0}{(9+86) \times 2+3} &:= \frac{7 \times (1+5) \times 40}{(9 \times 86-2) \times 3} &:= \frac{7 \times 15 \times 4+0}{9 \times 8 \times (6+2)+3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{72135}{94806} &:= \frac{7 \times (2+1-3+5)}{94-8 \times 06} &:= \frac{7 \times (2+1 \times 3+5)}{94-8+06} &:= \frac{7 \times (2+1^3) \times 5}{(-9+4 \times 8) \times 06} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{72369}{84150} &:= \frac{72+3+6 \times 9}{(8-4-1) \times 50} &:= \frac{7 \times 23+6 \times 9}{(8-4+1) \times 50} &:= \frac{7+2^3 \times 69}{(8+4+1) \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{72840}{96513} &:= \frac{(7-2) \times 8+40}{96-5 \times (1-3)} &:= \frac{(7-2) \times (8+40)}{9+6 \times 51+3} &:= \frac{(7+2-8) \times 40}{9+(6+5) \times (1+3)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{73692}{84105} &:= \frac{7^3-69+2}{8 \times 4 \times 10-5} &:= \frac{(7+3-6) \times 92}{84 \times 1 \times 05} &:= \frac{(7-3)^6 \times 92}{8^4 \times 105} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{73842}{90516} &:= \frac{7-3 \times (8-4^2)}{9 \times 05-1-6} &:= \frac{7 \times (3+8)+4^2}{90+(5-1) \times 6} &:= \frac{738+4+2}{905+1+6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{74259}{86301} &:= \frac{7-4+25+9}{8+6+30-1} &:= \frac{7+4+(2+5) \times 9}{86+3 \times 0 \times 1} &:= \frac{(7+(4+2) \times 5) \times 9}{86+301} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{76302}{81954} &:= \frac{7+6 \times 3+02}{8+1^9+5 \times 4} &:= \frac{76+30+2}{8 \times (1+9+5)-4} &:= \frac{7+6 \times 30+2}{(8-1) \times (9+5 \times 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{81360}{92547} &:= \frac{8 \times (1+3+6)+0}{9 \times (2+5)+4 \times 7} &:= \frac{(8+1+3) \times 60}{(9+2 \times 54) \times 7} &:= \frac{(8-1-3) \times 60}{((9-2) \times 5+4) \times 7}
 \end{aligned}$$

• Four Digit's Numerator

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{2364}{105789} &:= \frac{2 \times 3 - 6 + 4}{1 - (05 - 7) \times 89} &:= \frac{2 + 3 \times 6 + 4}{1057 + 8 + 9} &:= \frac{2 \times (3 + 6) \times 4}{(10 \times 5 \times 7 + 8) \times 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{2457}{103896} &:= \frac{(2 + 4 - 5) \times 7}{10 \times (38 - 9) + 6} &:= \frac{2 + 4 + 57}{10 \times 3 \times 89 - 6} &:= \frac{245 + 7}{(103 + 8) \times 96} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{2574}{103896} &:= \frac{2 + 5 \times 7 - 4}{1 + (03 + 8)^{9-6}} &:= \frac{2 + 57 - 4}{10 \times (3 \times 8 \times 9 + 6)} &:= \frac{2 \times (5 + 7 \times 4)}{10 \times 3 \times 89 - 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{2754}{108936} &:= \frac{2 + 7 \times (5 - 4)}{10 \times (8 + 9 \times 3) + 6} &:= \frac{2 + 7 + 5 + 4}{-1 \times 08 - 9 + 3^6} &:= \frac{2 + 75 + 4}{1 \times 089 \times 36} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{2796}{108345} &:= \frac{2 \times (7 - 9 + 6)}{10 \times (8 + 3 + 4 \times 5)} &:= \frac{2^{7-9+6}}{(1 \times 08 - 3)^4 - 5} &:= \frac{(2 + 7 + 9) \times 6}{(10 + 83) \times 45} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{3645}{107892} &:= \frac{(3 - 6 + 4) \times 5}{1 \times 07 \times 8 + 92} &:= \frac{3 + 6 - 4 + 5}{1 \times 07 + (8 + 9)^2} &:= \frac{(3 + 6 - 4) \times 5}{10 \times (7 \times 8 + 9 \times 2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4285}{103697} &:= \frac{4 - 2 + 8 + 5}{1 + 0369 - 7} &:= \frac{4 \times (2 + 8 - 5)}{1^{03} + 69 \times 7} &:= \frac{4 - 2 + 8 - 5}{(1 + 03) \times 6 + 97} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4293}{108756} &:= \frac{4 + 2 + 9 + 3}{(1 + (08 + 7) \times 5) \times 6} &:= \frac{4 + 29 - 3}{10 \times (87 - 5 - 6)} &:= \frac{4 + 2 + 9 \times 3}{10 \times (8 + 75) + 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4965}{108237} &:= \frac{(4 + 9 - 6) \times 5}{(108 - 2 + 3) \times 7} &:= \frac{4 + 96 + 5}{((10 + 8)^2 + 3) \times 7} &:= \frac{(4 - 9 + 6) \times 5}{108 + 2^3 - 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4985}{120637} &:= \frac{4 + 9 - 8 + 5}{1 \times 20 + 6 \times 37} &:= \frac{(4 + 9 + 8) \times 5}{(1 + 20 \times 6) \times 3 \times 7} &:= \frac{4 + (9 - 8)^5}{1 + 2 \times 06 \times (3 + 7)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5247}{103986} &:= \frac{5 - 2 \times (4 - 7)}{(1 + 03 \times 9) \times 8 - 6} &:= \frac{5 + 24 - 7}{1 + 03 + 9 \times 8 \times 6} &:= \frac{5 \times 2 \times 4 - 7}{((10 + 3) \times 9 - 8) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5724}{103986} &:= \frac{5 + 7 - 2 - 4}{10 - 3 + (9 + 8) \times 6} &:= \frac{5 + 7 + 24}{((10 + 3) \times 9 - 8) \times 6} &:= \frac{(5 \times 7 - 2) \times 4}{10 + 398 \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5973}{106428} &:= \frac{5 + (9 - 7) \times 3}{(106 - 4) \times 2 - 8} &:= \frac{5^{9-7} - 3}{(1 + 06 + 42) \times 8} &:= \frac{59 + 73}{(1 + 06) \times 42 \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6237}{104895} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 + 3 \times 7}{(10 \times (4 + 8) - 9) \times 5} &:= \frac{6 \times 2^3 + 7}{10 \times (4 + 89) - 5} &:= \frac{623 - 7}{10^4 + 8 \times 9 \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6573}{108924} &:= \frac{6 + 5 - 7 + 3}{(10 + 8 + 9 + 2) \times 4} &:= \frac{6 + 5 + 7 + 3}{(1 \times 089 - 2) \times 4} &:= \frac{6 + (5 + 7) \times 3}{10 \times (8 \times 9 - 2) - 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6579}{123840} &:= \frac{6 - 5 + 7 + 9}{1 + 2 - 3 + 8 \times 40} &:= \frac{(6 + 5) \times 7 - 9}{(1 + 23 + 8) \times 40} &:= \frac{6 \times (5 + 7 \times 9)}{1 \times 2 \times 3840} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6972}{103584} &:= \frac{6 \times 9 - 7 + 2}{103 + 5^{8-4}} &:= \frac{6 + 97 + 2}{10 \times 3 \times (5 + 8) \times 4} &:= \frac{6 \times (9 - 7) + 2}{(1 + 03) \times (5 + 8) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7524}{103968} &:= \frac{7 \times 5 - 24}{(1 + 03 + 9 + 6) \times 8} &:= \frac{7 \times 5 + 2 - 4}{(1 \times 03 + 9 \times 6) \times 8} &:= \frac{7 \times 5 \times 2 - 4}{(10 \times (3 + 9) - 6) \times 8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7560}{123984} &:= \frac{75-60}{1+2+3^{9-8+4}} &:= \frac{7 \times 5 \times 6 + 0}{(1 \times 2 + 39) \times 84} &:= \frac{(7-5) \times 60}{(1-2+3) \times 984} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7632}{105894} &:= \frac{7 \times 6 + 3 \times 2}{10 \times (58+9) - 4} &:= \frac{7+63+2}{105+894} &:= \frac{(7+6+3) \times 2}{((10+5) \times 8-9) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7956}{104832} &:= \frac{7 \times (9-5) + 6}{10 \times (48-3) - 2} &:= \frac{(7+95) \times 6}{(10+4) \times (8 \times 3)^2} &:= \frac{7 \times 9 + 56}{(1+048) \times 32} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9372}{105648} &:= \frac{9+37-2}{(10+56-4) \times 8} &:= \frac{9-3+7^2}{10 \times (5 \times 6 + 4 \times 8)} &:= \frac{9 \times (3+7) - 2}{(1+05 \times 6) \times 4 \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9526}{107384} &:= \frac{9+5+2+6}{10+7 \times (38-4)} &:= \frac{9 \times (5-2) + 6}{(10+7 \times 3) \times (8+4)} &:= \frac{9 \times 5^2 + 6}{(10+7 \times 3) \times 84} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9536}{108472} &:= \frac{9+53-6}{(1+08+4) \times 7^2} &:= \frac{9+5^3-6}{(108-4) \times 7 \times 2} &:= \frac{9 \times (5-3)^6}{(1+08)^4 - 7-2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9576}{120384} &:= \frac{9+5 \times (7-6)}{(1 \times 20 + 3 \times 8) \times 4} &:= \frac{9 - (5-7) \times 6}{12+03 \times 84} &:= \frac{(9+5-7) \times 6}{12 \times (03+8) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9786}{103452} &:= \frac{(9-7) \times (8+6)}{(103+45) \times 2} &:= \frac{9 \times 7 + 8 + 6}{(103 \times 4 - 5) \times 2} &:= \frac{9 \times (7+8+6)}{(10^3+4-5) \times 2}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.3 4 Equivalent Blocks

• Five Digit's Numerator

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10287}{59436} &:= \frac{1 \times 02 \times 8 - 7}{59-4+3-6} &:= \frac{1+02+8+7}{(5+9) \times (4+3) + 6} &:= \frac{10+2+8+7}{(5+9+4 \times 3) \times 6} &:= \frac{-1 \times 02 + 8 \times 7}{(59-4-3) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10368}{45792} &:= \frac{1-03+6+8}{4+(5-7+9)^2} &:= \frac{1 \times (-03+6) \times 8}{4 \times (5 \times 7 - 9) + 2} &:= \frac{1^{03} \times 6 \times 8}{4 \times (5 \times 7 + 9 \times 2)} &:= \frac{1+03+68}{4 \times 5 \times (7+9) - 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10527}{46893} &:= \frac{1+05-2+7}{4-6+(8+9) \times 3} &:= \frac{1+05+27}{46+8+93} &:= \frac{10+5 \times (2+7)}{4 \times 68 - 9 \times 3} &:= \frac{(1+05 \times 2) \times 7}{(4 \times 6 - 8 - 9)^3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10584}{37296} &:= \frac{1+05 \times (8-4)}{3+7 \times (2+9) - 6} &:= \frac{1+058+4}{37 \times 2 \times (9-6)} &:= \frac{1^{05} \times 84}{37 \times 2^{9-6}} &:= \frac{10 \times (5+8) - 4}{37 \times (2 \times 9 - 6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10675}{39284} &:= \frac{(1+06) \times 75}{3 \times (9^2 \times 8 - 4)} &:= \frac{10 \times 6 - 7 \times 5}{(39-2 \times 8) \times 4} &:= \frac{1^{06} \times 75}{3 \times ((9+2) \times 8 + 4)} &:= \frac{(10-6) \times 75}{3 \times 92 \times (8-4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10725}{36894} &:= \frac{-1 \times 07 + 2^5}{3 \times 6 + (8+9) \times 4} &:= \frac{(1+07 \times 2) \times 5}{(3-6) \times (8-94)} &:= \frac{10 \times (7-2+5)}{(3-6+89) \times 4} &:= \frac{(1+07) \times 25}{3+689-4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10752}{39648} &:= \frac{(10-7+5) \times 2}{3+(9-6+4) \times 8} &:= \frac{(1+07) \times 5 \times 2}{39+(6-4)^8} &:= \frac{10 \times 7 \times 5 + 2}{3-9+6^4+8} &:= \frac{(10-7+5)^2}{(3+9 \times 6) \times 4 + 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10845}{93267} &:= \frac{1+08-4+5}{9+(3+2+6) \times 7} &:= \frac{10 \times (8-4) - 5}{9 \times 32 + 6 + 7} &:= \frac{(10-8) \times 4 \times 5}{9+(3+2) \times 67} &:= \frac{1^{08} \times 45}{9 \times (3-2+6 \times 7)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10896}{52437} &:= \frac{1^{08} + 9 + 6}{5 + 2 \times (43 - 7)} &:= \frac{(1 - 08 + 9)^6}{5 + 2 + 43 \times 7} &:= \frac{1 + 089 + 6}{5^2 + 437} &:= \frac{10 + (8 + 9) \times 6}{(5 + 24 \times 3) \times 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12384}{96750} &:= \frac{(1 + 23 - 8) \times 4}{(9 - 6 + 7) \times 50} &:= \frac{12 \times 3 \times (8 - 4)}{(9 + 6) \times 75 + 0} &:= \frac{(1 + 23) \times (8 + 4)}{(9 - 6) \times 750} &:= \frac{1 \times 2^3 \times 84}{(9 + 6) \times 7 \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12389}{47650} &:= \frac{1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 8 - 9}{(4 - 7 + 6) \times 50} &:= \frac{1^2 + 3 \times (8 + 9)}{4 \times (7 - 6) \times 50} &:= \frac{1 - 2^3 + 8 \times 9}{(4 + 7 - 6) \times 50} &:= \frac{12 + 3 + 89}{(4 + 76) \times 5 + 0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12390}{48675} &:= \frac{1 \times 2 + 3 + 9 + 0}{(4 + 8 + 6 - 7) \times 5} &:= \frac{1 + 2 + 39 + 0}{4 + 86 + 75} &:= \frac{12 \times 3 + 90}{(4 \times 8 + 67) \times 5} &:= \frac{1^2 + 3 \times 9 + 0}{48 + 67 - 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12540}{73986} &:= \frac{1 \times 2 \times 5 + 40}{7 + 3 \times 98 - 6} &:= \frac{(1 + 2) \times 5 \times 4 + 0}{7^3 + 9 + 8 - 6} &:= \frac{1 \times 2 \times (5 + 40)}{7 \times (3 + 9 \times 8) + 6} &:= \frac{1 + 25 + 4 + 0}{73 + 98 + 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12798}{36450} &:= \frac{1 \times 2 \times (7 + 9 \times 8)}{3^{6-4} \times 50} &:= \frac{1^2 \times 79 \times 8}{(3 + 6) \times 4 \times 50} &:= \frac{1 \times 2 \times 79 \times 8}{3 \times 6 \times 4 \times 50} &:= \frac{(1 + 2) \times (7 + 9 \times 8)}{3^6 - 4 - 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12798}{54036} &:= \frac{1 \times 2 + 7 \times (9 - 8)}{5 \times 4 + 03 \times 6} &:= \frac{1 \times 2 + 7 + 9 \times 8}{(54 + 03) \times 6} &:= \frac{1 - 2 - 7 + 98}{5 \times (40 + 36)} &:= \frac{1 + 2 \times 7 \times 9 + 8}{5 \times (40 \times 3 - 6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12860}{73945} &:= \frac{12 \times (8 - 6) + 0}{73 + (9 + 4) \times 5} &:= \frac{1 \times 2^8 - 60}{7 \times (39 \times 4 + 5)} &:= \frac{12 - 8 + 60}{7^3 + (9 - 4) \times 5} &:= \frac{1 \times 28 \times 6 + 0}{7 \times 3 + 945} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12960}{37584} &:= \frac{1 - 2 - 9 + 60}{3 \times (7 + 5 \times 8) + 4} &:= \frac{1 + 29 + 60}{3 \times (7 \times (5 + 8) - 4)} &:= \frac{1 \times 2 \times (9 + 6) + 0}{3 - 7 \times (5 - 8) \times 4} &:= \frac{1 \times 2960}{37 \times 58 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13026}{48597} &:= \frac{1 \times 30 + 2 - 6}{(4 - 8 + 5) \times 97} &:= \frac{(1 + 3) \times 026}{485 - 97} &:= \frac{130 \times 2 \times 6}{(4 + 8) \times 5 \times 97} &:= \frac{13 \times 02 \times 6}{485 + 97} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{97524} &:= \frac{1 - 3 + 6 + 08}{9 - 7 \times (5 - 2^4)} &:= \frac{(-1 \times 3 + 6) \times 08}{(9 + 75) \times 2 + 4} &:= \frac{1 \times 3 \times (6 + 08)}{9 + (75 - 2) \times 4} &:= \frac{1^3 \times 6 \times 08}{(9 + 75 + 2) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13794}{65208} &:= \frac{1 \times 3 - (7 - 9) \times 4}{6 \times 5 \times 2 - 08} &:= \frac{(1 - 3) \times 7 + 9 \times 4}{(6 + 5 + 2) \times 08} &:= \frac{1 \times 3 \times (7 + 9) - 4}{6^{5-2} - 08} &:= \frac{1 \times 3^7 + 9 + 4}{65 \times 20 \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13904}{65728} &:= \frac{1 - 3 + 9 + 04}{6 + 5 + 7^2 - 8} &:= \frac{13 + 90 - 4}{6 \times (5 \times 7 \times 2 + 8)} &:= \frac{139 + 04}{6 \times 57 \times 2 - 8} &:= \frac{(1 - 3 + 90) \times 4}{(6 \times 5 \times 7 - 2) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13927}{58640} &:= \frac{(1 + 3 + 9) \times 2 - 7}{5 \times 8 \times (6 - 4) + 0} &:= \frac{13 + 9 \times 2 + 7}{5 \times (8 + 6 \times 4) + 0} &:= \frac{1 + 3 \times (9 \times 2 + 7)}{5 \times 8^{6-4} + 0} &:= \frac{(1 \times 3 + 92) \times 7}{5 \times (8 + 6) \times 40} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14058}{79236} &:= \frac{14 + 05 - 8}{7 \times (9 + 2 - 3) + 6} &:= \frac{14 + 0 \times 5 + 8}{7 + 9^2 + 36} &:= \frac{1 + 40 + 58}{7 \times 9^2 - 3 - 6} &:= \frac{140 - 5 + 8}{7 \times (9 + 2) + 3^6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14350}{26978} &:= \frac{(1 + 4 - 3) \times 50}{(2 - 6) \times (9 - 7 \times 8)} &:= \frac{1^4 \times 3 \times 50}{2 \times (6 + 9 \times (7 + 8))} &:= \frac{(1 + 4) \times 3 \times 50}{2 \times (697 + 8)} &:= \frac{(1 + 4 + 3) \times 50}{2 \times (6 \times 9 - 7) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14560}{73892} &:= \frac{1 + 45 - 6 + 0}{7 \times (3 + 8 + 9 \times 2)} &:= \frac{1 \times 4 \times 5 + 60}{7 \times (38 - 9) \times 2} &:= \frac{1 \times 4 \times 5 \times 6 + 0}{7 \times (3 - 8 + 92)} &:= \frac{(1^4 + 5) \times 60}{7 \times 3 \times (89 - 2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14806}{27593} &:= \frac{14 + 8 + 0 \times 6}{2 + 7 + 5 + 9 \times 3} &:= \frac{(-1 + 4 + 8) \times 06}{2 \times 75 - 9 \times 3} &:= \frac{148 + 06}{275 + 9 + 3} &:= \frac{1 \times 4 + 80 \times 6}{2 + 75 \times (9 + 3)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14935}{26780} &:= \frac{1 + 4 \times (9 + 3 - 5)}{2 - 6 + 7 \times 8 + 0} &:= \frac{1 + 49 + 3 + 5}{26 + 78 + 0} &:= \frac{1 - (4 - 9 \times 3) \times 5}{2 \times (6 + 7) \times 8 + 0} &:= \frac{1 \times 4 + 9 \times 35}{2 \times 6 + 7 \times 80}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15048}{39672} &:= \frac{15+04-8}{3 \times 9 - (6-7) \times 2} &:= \frac{1^5+04 \times 8}{3 \times (9+6+7 \times 2)} &:= \frac{1+50-4+8}{(3 \times 9-6) \times 7-2} &:= \frac{1+50+48}{3 \times (9+6+72)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15079}{24836} &:= \frac{1^5+07+9}{2 \times (4-8+3 \times 6)} &:= \frac{1 \times 50-7-9}{2 \times (4-8 \times (3-6))} &:= \frac{(1+5) \times 07+9}{2 \times (48-3)-6} &:= \frac{1+5+079}{2 \times (4+(8+3) \times 6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{42768} &:= \frac{1+53+09}{4 \times 27+68} &:= \frac{1+5^3+0 \times 9}{(4-2+7 \times 6) \times 8} &:= \frac{(1+5) \times 30+9}{4 \times (2^7+6)-8} &:= \frac{1+5+309}{4^2 \times (7+6 \times 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15486}{29370} &:= \frac{1 \times 5 - (4-8) \times 6}{2 \times 9+37+0} &:= \frac{1+5+4+8 \times 6}{(2+9) \times (3+7)+0} &:= \frac{1 \times 5-4+86}{2+93+70} &:= \frac{1+(5+48) \times 6}{2-9 \times (3-70)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15876}{43092} &:= \frac{15+(8-7) \times 6}{4^3-09+2} &:= \frac{1-(5-8) \times 7+6}{4 \times (30-9-2)} &:= \frac{(15-8) \times (7+6)}{4+3 \times 09^2} &:= \frac{1+5+(8-7)^6}{4-3+09 \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15930}{64782} &:= \frac{(1-5+9) \times 3+0}{64+7-8-2} &:= \frac{1 \times 5 \times (9-3)+0}{6+4+7 \times 8 \times 2} &:= \frac{1+59+30}{6 \times (4-7+8^2)} &:= \frac{(1^5+9) \times 30}{6^4-78+2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16790}{28543} &:= \frac{1-(6-7) \times 9+0}{2+8-5+4 \times 3} &:= \frac{(1+6) \times 7-9+0}{2 \times 8 \times 5-4 \times 3} &:= \frac{1^6+79+0}{2 \times (8+5 \times 4 \times 3)} &:= \frac{(1-6+7) \times 90}{2-8 \times (5-43)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16807}{94325} &:= \frac{1+6 \times 8+0 \times 7}{94 \times 3-2-5} &:= \frac{(1 \times 6+8) \times 07}{(9 \times 4 \times 3+2) \times 5} &:= \frac{(1+6 \times 8) \times 07}{(9 \times 43-2) \times 5} &:= \frac{(1+6) \times 8 \times 07}{9+4+3^{2+5}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16920}{83754} &:= \frac{1^{69} \times 20}{8+37+54} &:= \frac{(1-6+9) \times 20}{8 \times (3+7) \times 5-4} &:= \frac{(1+69) \times 2+0}{(8+3) \times 7 \times (5+4)} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 9 \times 20}{837+54} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16954}{70238} &:= \frac{1+6-9+5+4}{7+02 \times (3+8)} &:= \frac{1+6 \times (9-5)-4}{7^{02}+38} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times (9-5)+4}{70 \times 2-3 \times 8} &:= \frac{1 \times 6+9+5 \times 4}{70 \times 2-3+8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16983}{27540} &:= \frac{16+98-3}{(2+7) \times 5 \times 4+0} &:= \frac{1 \times 6+9 \times 8 \times 3}{(2 \times 7-5) \times 40} &:= \frac{(1-6) \times (9-83)}{2 \times 75 \times 4+0} &:= \frac{1+6 \times 98+3}{2 \times (7+5) \times 40} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17280}{49536} &:= \frac{17+28+0}{(4 \times 9+5) \times 3+6} &:= \frac{(1+7 \times 2) \times 8+0}{4 \times (95-3-6)} &:= \frac{172+8+0}{4 \times (9 \times 5 \times 3-6)} &:= \frac{(1^7+2) \times 80}{4-9 \times 5+3^6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17342}{95680} &:= \frac{1+(7+3+4) \times 2}{(9+5+6) \times 8+0} &:= \frac{1+73+42}{(9+5-6) \times 80} &:= \frac{1^7+(3 \times 4)^2}{(9-5+6) \times 80} &:= \frac{1 \times 73 \times 4-2}{(9+5+6) \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17820}{43659} &:= \frac{(1-7+8) \times 20}{(4-3+6) \times (5+9)} &:= \frac{1+7-8+20}{(4+3)^{6+5-9}} &:= \frac{1^7 \times 8 \times 20}{(4+3) \times (65-9)} &:= \frac{178+2+0}{(4+(3+6) \times 5) \times 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17820}{65934} &:= \frac{(1 \times 7+8) \times 2+0}{6+5 \times (9+3 \times 4)} &:= \frac{1+7-8+20}{6+5+9 \times (3+4)} &:= \frac{1^7 \times 8 \times 20}{6 \times (5+93)+4} &:= \frac{178+2+0}{659+3+4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18360}{49725} &:= \frac{1+83-60}{4-9+7 \times 2 \times 5} &:= \frac{18 \times 3-6+0}{4+9 \times (7+2+5)} &:= \frac{(1+8+3) \times 60}{(4 \times 97+2) \times 5} &:= \frac{(1^8+3) \times 60}{(4+9 \times 7 \times 2) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18540}{93627} &:= \frac{1^8 \times 5 \times 4+0}{9 \times 3 \times (6-2)-7} &:= \frac{1 \times 8 \times 5 \times 4+0}{936-2^7} &:= \frac{(1+8) \times 5 \times 4+0}{9 \times (3 \times 6^2-7)} &:= \frac{1^{85} \times 40}{9+3 \times 62+7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18603}{45792} &:= \frac{1 \times 8+6 \times 03}{4 \times (5-7+9 \times 2)} &:= \frac{(-1+8+6) \times 03}{4 \times (5 \times 7-9-2)} &:= \frac{1+8 \times 6+03}{4^{5+7-9} \times 2} &:= \frac{18+6^{03}}{4+5+7 \times 9^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18603}{52947} &:= \frac{1 \times 8+6 \times 03}{(5-2) \times 9+47} &:= \frac{(-1+8+6) \times 03}{(5-2) \times (9+4 \times 7)} &:= \frac{1+8 \times 6+03}{5 \times 29-4+7} &:= \frac{1 \times 8+60-3}{5 \times (2+(9-4) \times 7)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18620}{73549} &:= \frac{(1+8-6) \times 20}{7+3^5-4-9} &:= \frac{18+62+0}{73 \times 5-49} &:= \frac{1 \times 8+6 \times 2+0}{7-(3-5) \times 4 \times 9} &:= \frac{(1^8+6) \times 20}{7-3+549} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19035}{28764} &:= \frac{1+9+035}{2^{(8-7) \times 6}+4} &:= \frac{1 \times 90 \times (3+5)}{(2+8+7) \times 64} &:= \frac{1 \times 9 \times 03 \times 5}{2 \times 8 \times (7+6)-4} &:= \frac{1 \times 9 \times 035}{28+7 \times 64} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19465}{73280} &:= \frac{1+9-4+6+5}{(7+3-2) \times 8+0} &:= \frac{19+4+6+5}{(7+3^2) \times 8+0} &:= \frac{(1+9) \times (4+6 \times 5)}{(7+3^2) \times 80} &:= \frac{(1+9+4 \times 6) \times 5}{(7+3-2) \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19856}{32704} &:= \frac{1+9+8+5-6}{(3-2) \times 7 \times 4} &:= \frac{9 \times 8+5 \times 6}{3 \times 2 \times 7 \times 4} &:= \frac{(1+9) \times (8+5)+6}{32 \times 7-0 \times 4} &:= \frac{19 \times 8-5+6}{3^2 \times 7 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19872}{53406} &:= \frac{1+9-8+7 \times 2}{53-4-06} &:= \frac{1-9+8 \times (7-2)}{5+3^4+0 \times 6} &:= \frac{(1 \times 9+8+7) \times 2}{5^3+4-0 \times 6} &:= \frac{(1 \times 9+87) \times 2}{(5+3^4) \times 06} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20196}{74358} &:= \frac{2 \times (-01+9)+6}{7 \times 4 \times 3+5-8} &:= \frac{2 \times (01+9 \times 6)}{7 \times (4^3-5)-8} &:= \frac{2+0196}{(7-4)^{3-5+8}} &:= \frac{(2+01 \times 9) \times 6}{7 \times 43-58} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20631}{74589} &:= \frac{2+06+31}{7+45+89} &:= \frac{(20+6) \times 3 \times 1}{(7-4) \times (5+89)} &:= \frac{(20+6) \times (3+1)}{7+45 \times 8+9} &:= \frac{20 \times 6-3 \times 1}{((7+4) \times 5-8) \times 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{21054}{93786} &:= \frac{2+1 \times 05 \times 4}{(9-3+7) \times 8-6} &:= \frac{2+10+54}{(9-3) \times 7^{8-6}} &:= \frac{210+54}{(9+3) \times 7 \times (8+6)} &:= \frac{2+(1+05)^4}{(9^3-7) \times 8+6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{21380}{45967} &:= \frac{2+1 \times 38+0}{4+5 \times (9+6)+7} &:= \frac{2+1-3+80}{4-(5-9) \times 6 \times 7} &:= \frac{2+138+0}{(4+5 \times 9-6) \times 7} &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 3 \times 80}{4^5+9+6-7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{21504}{38976} &:= \frac{2^{1+5}+0 \times 4}{3+(8+9) \times 7-6} &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 50-4}{3 \times (8^9-7-6)} &:= \frac{2^{1^5 \times 04}}{38-9 \times (7-6)} &:= \frac{(2+1 \times 50) \times 4}{(38-9) \times (7+6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{21536}{87490} &:= \frac{2+1+5 \times (3+6)}{(8+7) \times (4+9)+0} &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times (5-3)^6}{8 \times (74-9)+0} &:= \frac{2 \times (1-5+36)}{8+7 \times 4 \times 9+0} &:= \frac{2^{1+5} \times 3 \times 6}{(8 \times 7-4) \times 90} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{21549}{78360} &:= \frac{2-1 \times 5+4 \times 9}{(7-8+3) \times 60} &:= \frac{(2+1 \times 5 \times 4) \times 9}{(7+8-3) \times 60} &:= \frac{2-1+5 \times (4+9)}{78 \times 3+6+0} &:= \frac{2 \times 154 \times 9}{7 \times 8 \times 3 \times 60} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{21697}{83450} &:= \frac{2-1+6 \times (9-7)}{8-3+45+0} &:= \frac{2 \times (1+6 \times (9-7))}{(8+3 \times 4) \times 5+0} &:= \frac{2 \times (1+6 \times 9)+7}{(8-3+4) \times 50} &:= \frac{2+1+6 \times 97}{(8-3) \times 450} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{21793}{50468} &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 7+9+3}{5 \times 04+68} &:= \frac{(2+1+7+9) \times 3}{50 \times 4-68} &:= \frac{2 \times (17-9)+3}{50-4+6-8} &:= \frac{2+1^7 \times 93}{5 \times (-04+6 \times 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{21835}{67490} &:= \frac{2 \times (1+8-3+5)}{6-7 \times 4+90} &:= \frac{2-1+8+35}{6 \times 7+4+90} &:= \frac{2 \times (1+8 \times 3)+5}{6+74+90} &:= \frac{21+83-5}{6^{7-4}+90} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{21960}{34587} &:= \frac{2 \times (1+9)+60}{34+5+87} &:= \frac{2 \times 1^9 \times 60}{((3+4) \times 5-8) \times 7} &:= \frac{(2+1+9) \times 60}{(34 \times 5-8) \times 7} &:= \frac{(2-1) \times 960}{3 \times (4+5) \times 8 \times 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23069}{58174} &:= \frac{2^3+06+9}{5+81-7 \times 4} &:= \frac{23 \times (-06+9)}{58 \times 1 \times (7-4)} &:= \frac{2-30 \times (6-9)}{58 \times (1+7-4)} &:= \frac{2+306-9}{58 \times (17-4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23571}{69840} &:= \frac{(2-3+5) \times 7-1}{(6+9) \times 8-40} &:= \frac{2 \times (35-7-1)}{(6+9) \times 8+40} &:= \frac{2+3+5+71}{6 \times (9-8) \times 40} &:= \frac{235+7+1}{(6+9) \times (8+40)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23598}{46170} &:= \frac{2^3 \times 5-9-8}{46-1^{70}} &:= \frac{2-3-5+98}{4+6+170} &:= \frac{2 \times 35-9+8}{4+61+70} &:= \frac{2+3 \times (5 \times 9+8)}{(46-1) \times 7+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25194}{67830} &:= \frac{2+5+1+9-4}{6+7-8+30} &:= \frac{2+5-(1-9) \times 4}{67+8+30} &:= \frac{(2+5-1) \times (9+4)}{6 \times 7 \times (8-3)+0} &:= \frac{(25+1) \times 9 \times 4}{(6+78) \times 30} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25408}{63917} &:= \frac{2+54+08}{6 \times (3 \times 9+1)-7} &:= \frac{2^5 \times 4+0 \times 8}{(6+39+1) \times 7} &:= \frac{(2^5+40) \times 8}{(6^3-9 \times 1) \times 7} &:= \frac{(2+54) \times 08}{(6 \times 3 \times 9-1) \times 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25467}{80319} &:= \frac{2 \times (5+4-6)+7}{8 \times (03+1)+9} &:= \frac{(2 \times 5+4) \times 6+7}{8+031 \times 9} &:= \frac{2 \times (5+4) \times (6+7)}{(80+3-1) \times 9} &:= \frac{2 \times (5-4) \times (6+7)}{80+3-1^9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25640}{37819} &:= \frac{(2+5-6) \times 40}{3+7 \times 8 \times 1^9} &:= \frac{2 \times (56+4)+0}{3 \times 7 \times 8 \times 1+9} &:= \frac{(2+5) \times 6 \times 40}{3 \times (7+819)} &:= \frac{(25-6) \times 40}{(3+7 \times 8) \times 19} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25973}{60148} &:= \frac{2 \times (5+9)+7+3}{(6+01+4) \times 8} &:= \frac{2-5+9 \times 7-3}{6 \times (014+8)} &:= \frac{2 \times (5+9 \times 7)-3}{60 \times (1+4)+8} &:= \frac{2 \times 5 \times (9+7+3)}{(60-1-4) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25974}{38610} &:= \frac{25+9+7-4}{3-8+6 \times 10} &:= \frac{2+5+9 \times 7 \times 4}{386-1+0} &:= \frac{(2+59) \times 74}{(3+8) \times 610} &:= \frac{(2 \times 59-7) \times 4}{(3+8) \times 6 \times 10} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{26481}{59073} &:= \frac{2+6+4 \times 8-1}{5+9+073} &:= \frac{2^6-4-8 \times 1}{5+90+7 \times 3} &:= \frac{26 \times (4+8-1)}{5+90 \times 7+3} &:= \frac{26 \times (48-1)}{5+907 \times 3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{26930}{45781} &:= \frac{2+6+9+3+0}{4 \times 5+7+8-1} &:= \frac{2 \times (6+9)+30}{45+7 \times 8+1} &:= \frac{2^6+9-3+0}{45-7+81} &:= \frac{(2-6+9) \times 30}{4^{5+7-8}-1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{27168}{39054} &:= \frac{2^{7-1+6-8}}{3 \times 9+0 \times 5-4} &:= \frac{2^{7+1 \times 6-8}}{3 \times (9+05)+4} &:= \frac{2-7+1+68}{3+90-5+4} &:= \frac{(27+1+6) \times 8}{390+5-4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{27531}{49680} &:= \frac{2+7+5^3-1}{(4 \times 9-6) \times 8+0} &:= \frac{2 \times (7+5^3+1)}{4 \times (9+6) \times 8+0} &:= \frac{(2^7+5) \times (3+1)}{4 \times (9-6) \times 80} &:= \frac{2 \times ((7+5)^3+1)}{(4+9) \times 6 \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{27531}{86940} &:= \frac{2+7 \times (5+3)-1}{86+94+0} &:= \frac{2 \times (7 \times 5+3 \times 1)}{8 \times 6 \times (9-4)+0} &:= \frac{2+75 \times (3-1)}{8 \times (6+9) \times 4+0} &:= \frac{2+75 \times 3+1}{(8-6) \times 9 \times 40} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{27540}{39168} &:= \frac{27 \times 5 \times 4+0}{3 \times (9-1-6)^8} &:= \frac{(2+7) \times 5 \times 4+0}{(39-1-6) \times 8} &:= \frac{27 \times (5+40)}{(3+9)^{1-6+8}} &:= \frac{(2+7) \times (5+40)}{(3+9 \times 1) \times 6 \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{27594}{30618} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 5+9 \times 4}{(3+06) \times (1+8)} &:= \frac{2^7+5+9+4}{3 \times 06 \times (1+8)} &:= \frac{2-7 \times (5-9 \times 4)}{3^{06-1^8}} &:= \frac{(27+5) \times 9+4}{3 \times 06 \times 18} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{27810}{54693} &:= \frac{2 \times (7+8 \times 1)+0}{5-(4-6) \times 9 \times 3} &:= \frac{2+7+81+0}{(5 \times (4+6)+9) \times 3} &:= \frac{2^7-8 \times 1+0}{5 \times 46+9-3} &:= \frac{(2^7-8) \times 10}{5 \times (469+3)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29145}{76380} &:= \frac{(2-9 \times (1-4)) \times 5}{(7-6) \times 380} &:= \frac{29+145}{76+380} &:= \frac{29 \times 1 \times 4 \times 5}{7 \times 6^3+8+0} &:= \frac{29 \times (1+4 \times 5)}{7 \times 6 \times 38+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29160}{37584} &:= \frac{29+16+0}{3-7+58+4} &:= \frac{29+1+60}{(3+7+5) \times 8-4} &:= \frac{(29+1) \times 6+0}{((3+7) \times 5+8) \times 4} &:= \frac{(29+1) \times 60}{(3+7) \times 58 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29187}{30456} &:= \frac{2 \times (9-1^8)+7}{(3-04+5) \times 6} &:= \frac{2 \times (9-1+8+7)}{(3+0 \times 4+5) \times 6} &:= \frac{291-8-7}{(3+045) \times 6} &:= \frac{(2+918) \times 7}{30 \times 4 \times 56} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29187}{63450} &:= \frac{2+91-8+7}{(6+34) \times 5+0} &:= \frac{291-8-7}{(6-3) \times 4 \times 50} &:= \frac{2+9 \times 1 \times 8 \times 7}{(6^3+4) \times 5+0} &:= \frac{29-1+87}{(6+3-4) \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29376}{50184} &:= \frac{2 \times (9+3 \times (7-6))}{5+(01+8) \times 4} &:= \frac{2 \times (9+3 \times 7-6)}{50+1 \times 8 \times 4} &:= \frac{2 \times (9+3 \times (7+6))}{(50-1-8) \times 4} &:= \frac{2 \times (9+3) \times (7+6)}{501+8 \times 4}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29376}{51840} &:= \frac{2 \times (93 - 76)}{5 \times 1 \times (8 + 4) + 0} &:= \frac{2^{9-3} - 7 - 6}{5 + 1 + 84 + 0} &:= \frac{2 \times (93 - 7 \times 6)}{5 \times (1 + 8) \times 4 + 0} &:= \frac{2^9 - 376}{5 \times 1 \times (8 + 40)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29406}{37518} &:= \frac{29 \times 4 + 0 \times 6}{37 \times (5 - 1^8)} &:= \frac{(2 \times 9 + 40) \times 6}{37 \times (5 - 1 + 8)} &:= \frac{29 + 4 \times 0 \times 6}{3 + 7 \times (5 + 1) - 8} &:= \frac{29 + 406}{37 + 518} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29637}{40851} &:= \frac{296 + 37}{408 + 51} &:= \frac{2 \times (9 \times (6 + 3) - 7)}{4 \times (0 \times 8 + 51)} &:= \frac{(2 \times 9 - 6) \times 37}{(4 + 08) \times 51} &:= \frac{296 - 37}{408 - 51} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29673}{80541} &:= \frac{2 + 9 + 6 \times (7 - 3)}{80 + 5 \times (4 - 1)} &:= \frac{2 + 9 + 6 \times 7 + 3}{8 \times (05 \times 4 - 1)} &:= \frac{(2 - 9 + 6 \times 7) \times 3}{80 + 5 \times 41} &:= \frac{(2 + 9 \times 6) \times (7 + 3)}{80 \times (5 \times 4 - 1)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29861}{73504} &:= \frac{2 + 9 + 8 - 6 \times 1}{(-7 + 3 \times 5) \times 04} &:= \frac{(2 + 9) \times (8 + 6 - 1)}{7^3 + 5 + 04} &:= \frac{(2 \times 9)^{8-6} + 1}{(7 - 3) \times 50 \times 4} &:= \frac{2 + 9 + 8 + 6 + 1}{7 + 3 + 50 + 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30158}{49672} &:= \frac{3 + 01 + 5 + 8}{4 + 9 + 6 + 7 + 2} &:= \frac{30 + 1 - 5 + 8}{4 + 9 - 6 + 7^2} &:= \frac{3 + (01 + 5) \times 8}{4 \times (9 - 6) + 72} &:= \frac{(30 - 1) \times 5 + 8}{4 \times (9 + 6 \times (7 + 2))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30492}{81675} &:= \frac{3 + (-04 + 9)^2}{(8 + 1^6 \times 7) \times 5} &:= \frac{3 \times 04 \times (9 - 2)}{(8 + 1 - 6) \times 75} &:= \frac{30 \times (4 + 9) + 2}{(8 + 1 \times 6) \times 75} &:= \frac{30 + (4 + 9) \times 2}{(8 - 1 \times 6) \times 75} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30495}{82176} &:= \frac{3^{04} + 9 + 5}{(8 \times 2)^{1+7-6}} &:= \frac{3 \times 04 \times 95}{8^{2+17} \times 6} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 \times 4 + 95)}{8 \times 2 \times (1 + 7) \times 6} &:= \frac{(30 - 4) \times 95}{8^{2+1} \times (7 + 6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31062}{48597} &:= \frac{(3 - 1)^{06} - 2}{(4 - 8 + 5) \times 97} &:= \frac{310 \times 6 \times 2}{(4 + 8) \times 5 \times 97} &:= \frac{(3 + 1) \times 062}{485 - 97} &:= \frac{31 \times 06 \times 2}{485 + 97} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31248}{95760} &:= \frac{3^{1+2} - 4 + 8}{95 \times (7 - 6) + 0} &:= \frac{31 + 248}{9 \times (5 \times 7 + 60)} &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 248}{(9 \times 5 - 7) \times 60} &:= \frac{31 \times (24 + 8)}{(9 - 5) \times 760} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31426}{57890} &:= \frac{3 - 1 + 42 - 6}{5 - 7 + 8 \times 9 + 0} &:= \frac{3 \times (1 + 4^2) + 6}{(5 + 7) \times 8 + 9 + 0} &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 4 + 2^6}{5 + (7 + 8) \times 9 + 0} &:= \frac{3 + (1 + 4) \times 2^6}{5 \times 7 \times (8 + 9) + 0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31724}{98056} &:= \frac{3 - 1 + (7 - 2) \times 4}{98 - 05 \times 6} &:= \frac{3 - 1 + 7 + 24}{(9 + 8 + 0 \times 5) \times 6} &:= \frac{3 \times (17 + 2^4)}{9 \times (8 \times 05 - 6)} &:= \frac{(3 + 17)^2 - 4}{9 \times (80 + 56)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31860}{59472} &:= \frac{3 + 18 - 6 + 0}{5 \times (9 + 4 - 7) - 2} &:= \frac{3 \times 1 \times 8 + 6 + 0}{5 \times (9 + 4) - 7 - 2} &:= \frac{3 \times (1 + 8 + 6) + 0}{(5 + 9 + 4 \times 7) \times 2} &:= \frac{3 \times 18 + 6 + 0}{59 + 4 + 7^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31950}{72846} &:= \frac{(3 + 1 \times 9) \times 50}{(7^2 + 8) \times 4 \times 6} &:= \frac{(3 + 1^9) \times 50}{(72 + 8 - 4) \times 6} &:= \frac{(3 + 1) \times 9 \times 50}{7 \times 2 + 8^4 - 6} &:= \frac{3 \times 1^9 \times 50}{(7 + 2) \times (8 \times 4 + 6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{32175}{48906} &:= \frac{(3 + (2 - 1) \times 7) \times 5}{4 + 8 \times 9 + 0 \times 6} &:= \frac{3 - 2 - 1 + 75}{(4 + 8) \times 9 + 06} &:= \frac{3 + 217 + 5}{(48 + 9) \times 06} &:= \frac{(3 + 2 - 1) \times 75}{(4 + 8 \times 9) \times 06} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{34251}{97860} &:= \frac{3 \times (4 - 2 + 5 \times 1)}{(9 - 7 + 8) \times 6 + 0} &:= \frac{3^4 \times 2 + 5 + 1}{(9 + 7 - 8) \times 60} &:= \frac{342 - 5 - 1}{(9 - 7) \times 8 \times 60} &:= \frac{3 \times 42 \times (5 - 1)}{(9 + (7 + 8)) \times 60} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{34596}{78120} &:= \frac{3 - 4 + 5^{9-6}}{(7 + 8 - 1) \times 20} &:= \frac{3 + 4 - (5 - 9) \times 6}{7 \times (8 + 1 \times 2) + 0} &:= \frac{3 \times (4 \times 5 \times 9 + 6)}{7 \times (8 + 1) \times 20} &:= \frac{3 \times 4^5 - 96}{7 \times (8 \times 120)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{34986}{57120} &:= \frac{3^4 + 9 \times 8 - 6}{(5 + 7 \times 1) \times 20} &:= \frac{3 - (4 - 9) \times 8 + 6}{5 \times (7 + 1) \times 2 + 0} &:= \frac{(3 \times 4 + 9)^{8-6}}{(5 \times 7 + 1) \times 20} &:= \frac{3 \times (4 \times 9 \times 8 + 6)}{(5 + 7) \times 120} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{35489}{61720} &:= \frac{3 - 5 \times 4 \times (8 - 9)}{6 + 17 \times 2 + 0} &:= \frac{3 \times 54 + 8 - 9}{(6 + 1 + 7) \times 20} &:= \frac{(3 - 5 \times (4 - 8)) \times 9}{(6 - 1) \times 72 + 0} &:= \frac{3 \times (5 + 4 \times 8 + 9)}{(6 - (1 - 7)) \times 20}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{35640}{91872} &:= \frac{3 \times (5+6+4) + 0}{(9 - (1-8) \times 7) \times 2} &:= \frac{35 + 640}{(9+1) \times 87 \times 2} &:= \frac{3 \times (56+4) + 0}{(9-1) \times (8 \times 7 + 2)} &:= \frac{(3 \times 5)^{6-4} + 0}{(9+1) \times (8 \times 7 + 2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{35802}{97461} &:= \frac{3+5+8+02}{9-7+46+1} &:= \frac{(3-5+8)^{02}}{9+7 \times 4+61} &:= \frac{3 \times 5 \times (8-02)}{9 \times 7 \times 4-6-1} &:= \frac{358+02}{974+6 \times 1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{36025}{41789} &:= \frac{3 \times 6+02+5}{4+1+7+8+9} &:= \frac{(3+6 \times 02) \times 5}{4+1-7+89} &:= \frac{(3+6) \times 025}{(4+17+8) \times 9} &:= \frac{3 \times (60 \times 2+5)}{(4+1) \times (78+9)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{36207}{54981} &:= \frac{3 \times 6^2+0 \times 7}{5 \times 49-81} &:= \frac{3+6+207}{(5+4 \times 9) \times 8 \times 1} &:= \frac{3^{6 \times 2-07}}{(5+4 \times 9) \times (8+1)} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 \times (20+7)}{5+4+9 \times 81} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{36720}{48195} &:= \frac{(3+6+7) \times 2+0}{4-8+1+9 \times 5} &:= \frac{(3-6+7) \times 20}{(4+8+1 \times 9) \times 5} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 \times 7+2+0}{(4+8 \times 1) \times (9+5)} &:= \frac{(3+6+7) \times 20}{(4+8 \times (1+9)) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{36897}{51204} &:= \frac{(3+6 \times 8-9) \times 7}{51 \times 2 \times 04} &:= \frac{3+6 \times 8-9+7}{(5+12) \times 04} &:= \frac{3 \times (6+8)^{9-7}}{51 \times 2^{04}} &:= \frac{(3+6 \times (8+9)) \times 7}{5 \times 1 \times 204} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{37185}{92460} &:= \frac{37 \times 1 \times (8-5)}{9 \times 24+60} &:= \frac{3 \times (71+8 \times 5)}{9 \times 2 \times 46+0} &:= \frac{3 \times (71+8-5)}{92+460} &:= \frac{37 \times 18 \times 5}{9 \times 2 \times 460} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{37250}{61984} &:= \frac{3+72+50}{6+198+4} &:= \frac{(3+7) \times 25+0}{(6+1 \times 98) \times 4} &:= \frac{(3+72) \times 5+0}{(61-9) \times (8+4)} &:= \frac{(3+7) \times 2 \times 50}{(61-9) \times 8 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{37485}{92610} &:= \frac{(3 \times 7-4) \times (8-5)}{9 \times 2 \times (6+1)+0} &:= \frac{3-7+4+85}{(9+2 \times 6) \times 10} &:= \frac{3+7+4+8-5}{(9-2) \times 6 \times 1+0} &:= \frac{3+7+4 \times 8 \times 5}{(9-2) \times 6 \times 10} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{37590}{81624} &:= \frac{3 \times 7+5+9+0}{8 \times (1+6+2)+4} &:= \frac{3+7+5+90}{(8+(1+6)^2) \times 4} &:= \frac{(3-7) \times 5+90}{8 \times (1-6+24)} &:= \frac{3 \times 7 \times 5 \times 9+0}{8 \times 16^2+4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{38259}{46107} &:= \frac{3+8+2 \times (5+9)}{46+1^{07}} &:= \frac{3+8 \times 2+59}{4 \times 6+10 \times 7} &:= \frac{3+(8-2) \times 5 \times 9}{(46+1) \times 07} &:= \frac{(382-5) \times 9}{4^6 \times 1-07} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{38907}{41265} &:= \frac{3 \times 8+9+0 \times 7}{4-1+2+6 \times 5} &:= \frac{3+89+07}{(4+1) \times (26-5)} &:= \frac{(3 \times 8+9) \times 07}{(41+2+6) \times 5} &:= \frac{3 \times (8+90 \times 7)}{(412-6) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{40281}{76395} &:= \frac{40-2-8-1}{7+6+3 \times (9+5)} &:= \frac{40+2 \times (8+1)}{76+39-5} &:= \frac{4+02+81}{7+63+95} &:= \frac{4 \times (028+1)}{(7+6 \times 3) \times 9-5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{40293}{81675} &:= \frac{4+(02+9) \times 3}{(8+1^6 \times 7) \times 5} &:= \frac{40 \times 2-9+3}{(8-1 \times 6) \times 75} &:= \frac{40+293}{(8 \times 16+7) \times 5} &:= \frac{40+2^9+3}{(8+1+6) \times 75} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{40635}{71982} &:= \frac{(4+06-3) \times 5}{7-1 \times 9+8^2} &:= \frac{(40+6+3) \times 5}{(7-1) \times 9 \times 8+2} &:= \frac{(4+06) \times 35}{(71-9) \times (8+2)} &:= \frac{40 \times (6+3+5)}{(71-9) \times 8 \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{40851}{63279} &:= \frac{(4+08) \times 51}{(6+3 \times 2) \times 79} &:= \frac{4 \times (08+5)-1}{(6-3-2) \times 79} &:= \frac{408-51}{(6+3-2) \times 79} &:= \frac{408+51}{632+79} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{40851}{73692} &:= \frac{4 \times (0 \times 8+51)}{(7+3-6) \times 92} &:= \frac{4 \times (08+5)-1}{(7-3+6) \times 9+2} &:= \frac{408-51}{7+3^6-92} &:= \frac{408+51}{7+3^6+92} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{40976}{58312} &:= \frac{4+09+7+6}{5+8 \times (3+1^2)} &:= \frac{4 \times (0 \times 9+7+6)}{(5+8 \times (3+1)) \times 2} &:= \frac{4 \times (09)+7 \times 6}{(5 \times 8-3) \times (1+2)} &:= \frac{4 \times (097-6)}{5+8^3+1^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41038}{67592} &:= \frac{(4-1) \times 03+8}{6+(7-5+9) \times 2} &:= \frac{(4+10) \times 3-8}{6-7+59-2} &:= \frac{4 \times 10+3+8}{6 \times (7-5) \times (9-2)} &:= \frac{4 \times (10+3 \times 8)}{(67+5 \times 9) \times 2}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41520}{73698} &:= \frac{4 \times 15 + 20}{(7+3) \times (6+9) - 8} &:= \frac{(4-1+5) \times 20}{(7-3) \times 69 + 8} &:= \frac{4 \times 15 \times 20}{7^3 \times 6 + 9 \times 8} &:= \frac{4 \times 1 \times 5 \times 2 + 0}{7 + 3 + 69 - 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42816}{73590} &:= \frac{4 \times 2^{8+1-6}}{7+3+5 \times 9+0} &:= \frac{4 \times 2 \times 8 \times 1^6}{(7-3) \times 5 + 90} &:= \frac{4 + 2 \times 81 - 6}{73 \times 5 - 90} &:= \frac{(4+2) \times 81 - 6}{735 + 90} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42930}{81567} &:= \frac{4^2 - 9 + 3 + 0}{(8-1-5) \times 6 + 7} &:= \frac{(4^2 - 9) \times 30}{8-1+56 \times 7} &:= \frac{4 \times (2+93) + 0}{(8-1 \times 5)^6 - 7} &:= \frac{4 + 29 - 3 + 0}{8 + 1 \times 56 - 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{43602}{51987} &:= \frac{4^3 - 6 \times 02}{5 \times (19-8) + 7} &:= \frac{4 + (3+60) \times 2}{5 + (1+9) \times (8+7)} &:= \frac{4 \times (3+6^{02})}{51+9 \times (8+7)} &:= \frac{4 + 3 \times 60 \times 2}{((5+1) \times 9+8) \times 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{43875}{91260} &:= \frac{(4+3+8) \times 7 - 5}{(9-1) \times 26 + 0} &:= \frac{4 + (3+8)^{7-5}}{(9+1) \times 26 + 0} &:= \frac{(4+3+8) \times 7 \times 5}{91 \times 2 \times 6 + 0} &:= \frac{(4+3+8) \times 75}{9 \times 1 \times 260} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{45279}{63180} &:= \frac{4 \times 5 + 2 \times 7 + 9}{6 \times (3-1+8) + 0} &:= \frac{4^5 \times 2 + 7 + 9}{6^{3-1} \times 80} &:= \frac{(45-2) \times (7+9)}{6 \times (3-1) \times 80} &:= \frac{4 + 5 + 2^7 \times 9}{(6+3) \times 180} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{45738}{60291} &:= \frac{4 + 5 + 7 \times 3 - 8}{60 \times 2 - 91} &:= \frac{45 + 7^3 + 8}{(60-2) \times 9 \times 1} &:= \frac{(45+7+3) \times 8}{(60-2) \times (9+1)} &:= \frac{4 - (5-7 \times 3) \times 8}{6 \times 029 \times 1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{46023}{58719} &:= \frac{4 \times (6+02) - 3}{5 \times 8 + 7 - 1 - 9} &:= \frac{4 + 60 + 23}{5 + 87 + 19} &:= \frac{4 + 60 - 2 \times 3}{5 \times (8+7) - 1^9} &:= \frac{4 + 602 + 3}{58 + 719} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{46971}{58023} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 9 - 7 \times 1}{(5+8 \times 02) \times 3} &:= \frac{4 \times (6+9) + 7 + 1}{5 + 80 + 2 - 3} &:= \frac{469 + 7 \times 1}{580 + 2^3} &:= \frac{4 \times (6-9+7) + 1}{5 + 8 + 02^3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{48725}{91603} &:= \frac{4 - 8 + 7^2 + 5}{91 + 6 - 03} &:= \frac{(4-8+7) \times 25}{9 \times 16 - 03} &:= \frac{4 \times (8+7+2 \times 5)}{9-1+60 \times 3} &:= \frac{4 \times (8+72) + 5}{9-1+603} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{49038}{51267} &:= \frac{4 \times 9 + 0 \times 3 + 8}{5 + 1 - 2 + 6 \times 7} &:= \frac{4 \times (9+03 \times 8)}{5-1+2 \times 67} &:= \frac{4 \times (90-3 \times 8)}{(5-1) \times (2+67)} &:= \frac{4 \times 9 \times (03+8)}{(5+1) \times (2+67)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{49536}{71208} &:= \frac{4+9 \times (5-3) - 6}{7+1 \times 2 \times 08} &:= \frac{4 \times (9 \times (5-3) - 6)}{71-2+0 \times 8} &:= \frac{(49+5 \times 3) \times 6}{(71-2) \times 08} &:= \frac{49-5 \times (3-6)}{7 \times 12 + 08} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{49680}{57132} &:= \frac{4+96-80}{5+7+13-2} &:= \frac{(4+9-6) \times 80}{5+71 \times 3^2} &:= \frac{(4-9+6) \times 80}{5 \times (7-1) \times 3+2} &:= \frac{4 \times (9+6+80)}{5+(7-1)^3 \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{50274}{81396} &:= \frac{5 \times (-02+7) - 4}{8-1+3^{9-6}} &:= \frac{50-2^{7-4}}{8+(1^3+9) \times 6} &:= \frac{50+2+7+4}{8+1-3+96} &:= \frac{50+2+74}{(8-1+3 \times 9) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{51408}{92736} &:= \frac{51+408}{9 \times (2^7-36)} &:= \frac{51 \times (4-0 \times 8)}{92 \times (7+3-6)} &:= \frac{51+4 \times 0 \times 8}{9^2-7+3 \times 6} &:= \frac{5+140+8}{9+273-6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{53176}{92480} &:= \frac{53-1^7-6}{(9-2 \times 4) \times 80} &:= \frac{5+(3-1^7)^6}{(9+2+4) \times 8+0} &:= \frac{(5-3 \times (1-7)) \times 6}{(9-2-4) \times 80} &:= \frac{(5+317) \times 6}{(9-2) \times 480} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{53406}{81972} &:= \frac{53-4-06}{8+1 \times 9+7^2} &:= \frac{5+3^4+0 \times 6}{8-(1-9 \times 7) \times 2} &:= \frac{(5+3^4) \times 06}{8 \times 1 \times (97+2)} &:= \frac{5 \times (3+40) \times 6}{8+1972} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{54306}{89217} &:= \frac{5+43-06}{8 \times 9-2-1^7} &:= \frac{5 \times 4+30+6}{8-(9-21) \times 7} &:= \frac{5 \times (4+3) \times 06}{89+2^{1+7}} &:= \frac{5 \times (4^3+06)}{8+9^2 \times 1 \times 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{54912}{87360} &:= \frac{5-4+9+12}{8+7 \times 3+6+0} &:= \frac{5+49+12}{87+3 \times 6+0} &:= \frac{(54-9-1) \times 2}{8 \times (7+3) + 60} &:= \frac{54 \times (9+1 \times 2)}{(8+7) \times (3+60)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{58941}{63720} &:= \frac{5 + (8+9) \times 4 + 1}{6 + 37 \times 2 + 0} &:= \frac{58 + 941}{6^3 \times (7-2) + 0} &:= \frac{(5-8+9)^4 - 1}{(63+7) \times 20} &:= \frac{5 + 8 \times (9-4-1)}{(6+3-7) \times 20} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{60324}{79518} &:= \frac{(6+03) \times 2 + 4}{7+9-5+18} &:= \frac{(6+03+2) \times 4}{7 \times 9 - 5 \times 1^8} &:= \frac{6 \times (03+2 \times 4)}{(7+9) \times 5 - 1 + 8} &:= \frac{60 + 32 - 4}{7 \times (9+5) + 18} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{60741}{89325} &:= \frac{6+07+4 \times 1}{(8-9+3 \times 2) \times 5} &:= \frac{6+07 \times 4 \times 1}{8 + (9-3) \times (2+5)} &:= \frac{(6+07) \times 4 - 1}{8 \times (9+3-2) - 5} &:= \frac{607 + 4 + 1}{893 + 2 + 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{61074}{85293} &:= \frac{61-07+4}{(8+5 \times 2+9) \times 3} &:= \frac{6+10 \times (7+4)}{(8-5) \times 2 \times 9 \times 3} &:= \frac{6 \times 107 - 4}{(8+5^2) \times 9 \times 3} &:= \frac{6 \times (1+07 \times 4)}{(8-5)^2 \times 9 \times 3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{61075}{92834} &:= \frac{(6-1^{07}) \times 5}{9+28-3+4} &:= \frac{(6-1) \times 07 \times 5}{9+2^8-3+4} &:= \frac{6 \times 10 \times 7 + 5}{(9+2+8) \times 34} &:= \frac{6 \times 1 \times 075}{9 \times (2 \times 8 + 3) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{61203}{98457} &:= \frac{6+1 \times 20-3}{98-4-57} &:= \frac{(6+1)^2 - 03}{9 \times (8-4+5) - 7} &:= \frac{6 + (1+20) \times 3}{98+4 \times 5 - 7} &:= \frac{(6+1) \times (20+3)}{(9+8+4 \times 5) \times 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{61397}{85204} &:= \frac{6 \times (1+3 \times (9+7))}{8+5 \times 20 \times 4} &:= \frac{6+1 - (3-9) \times 7}{8 - (5-20) \times 4} &:= \frac{(6+1^3) \times 9 \times 7}{(8-5) \times 204} &:= \frac{(6+1) \times 39 \times 7}{(8+5) \times 204} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{63504}{89712} &:= \frac{6+3+50+4}{8+9 \times (7+1 \times 2)} &:= \frac{63 \times 5 + 0 \times 4}{89 \times (7-1 \times 2)} &:= \frac{63 \times (5+04)}{89 \times (7+1 \times 2)} &:= \frac{(6+3) \times 504}{8 + (9+71)^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{63512}{70984} &:= \frac{6+3+5+1+2}{7+0 \times 9+8+4} &:= \frac{6+3 \times 5 \times (1+2)}{70-9-8+4} &:= \frac{6+3^{5-1}-2}{7 \times 09+8 \times 4} &:= \frac{(6^3+5) \times (1+2)}{709+8 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{68170}{94235} &:= \frac{6-8+1 \times 70}{9 \times (4 \times 2+3) - 5} &:= \frac{68 \times 17 + 0}{94 \times (2+3 \times 5)} &:= \frac{68 \times 1 \times 70}{94 \times 2 \times 35} &:= \frac{68 + 170}{94 + 235} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{71085}{93426} &:= \frac{(7-1+08) \times 5}{(9+34) \times 2+6} &:= \frac{7 \times 10 \times (8-5)}{((9+3) \times 4-2) \times 6} &:= \frac{7 \times 1 \times 08 \times 5}{93 \times 4 + 2 - 6} &:= \frac{7 \times (1+08) \times 5}{9 \times (34+2 \times 6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{71254}{96038} &:= \frac{7 + (1-2+5) \times 4}{9+60-38} &:= \frac{7-1+2 \times 5 \times 4}{9 \times 6+0 \times 3+8} &:= \frac{7^{1 \times 2} + 5 \times 4}{9+60+3 \times 8} &:= \frac{7 \times (1+2+5 \times 4)}{9+6^{03}-8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{72693}{85104} &:= \frac{72+6 \times 9-3}{8 \times 5+104} &:= \frac{7+2 \times (6+93)}{8 \times 5 \times (10-4)} &:= \frac{7-2+6 \times (9-3)}{8 \times (5+1^{04})} &:= \frac{7+2^6+93}{8 \times (5+1) \times 04} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{72864}{93150} &:= \frac{72 \times (8 \times 6-4)}{9 \times 3 \times 150} &:= \frac{728-6 \times 4}{9 \times (3-1) \times 50} &:= \frac{7 \times 2 \times 8 + 6^4}{9 \times (3+1) \times 50} &:= \frac{(7 \times 2+8) \times 6^4}{9^{3 \times 1} \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{75106}{83942} &:= \frac{7+5-1+06}{8+3 \times 9-4^2} &:= \frac{7 \times (5-1) + 06}{8-3-9+42} &:= \frac{7+5 \times 10-6}{83-(9+4) \times 2} &:= \frac{75-1-06}{83+9-4^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{76314}{82950} &:= \frac{7 \times 6+3+1^4}{(8+2-9) \times 50} &:= \frac{7+63-1^4}{(8-2+9) \times 5+0} &:= \frac{7 \times (6 \times 3-1) - 4}{(8 \times 2+9) \times 5+0} &:= \frac{7+63 \times (1+4)}{(8 \times 2-9) \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{78246}{95013} &:= \frac{7 \times (8-2+4-6)}{9+5^{-01+3}} &:= \frac{7 \times (8-2 \times 4+6)}{9 \times (5+01) - 3} &:= \frac{7 \times (8 \times (2+4)+6)}{9 \times (50+1^3)} &:= \frac{7 \times 8 \times (2 \times 4+6)}{950-1+3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{79650}{81243} &:= \frac{(7+9-6) \times 5+0}{8 \times 1 \times (2+4)+3} &:= \frac{7 \times (9+6) - 5+0}{81+24-3} &:= \frac{(7-9+6) \times 50}{(8^{1 \times 2} + 4) \times 3} &:= \frac{7 + (9-6)^5 + 0}{((8+1)^2 + 4) \times 3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{80712}{93456} &:= \frac{8+07^{1 \times 2}}{9-3+4+56} &:= \frac{80-7+1+2}{(9+3-4) \times (5+6)} &:= \frac{(8 \times 07+1) \times 2}{9+3+4 \times 5 \times 6} &:= \frac{8 \times (07+12)}{(9+3+4) \times (5+6)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{87120}{93654} &:= \frac{8 \times (7+1+2)+0}{(9+3+6) \times 5-4} &:= \frac{8+712+0}{9 \times (3 \times 6 \times 5-4)} &:= \frac{(8+7-1) \times 20}{9 \times 3 \times (6+5)+4} &:= \frac{(8+7+1) \times 20}{9 \times 36+5 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{87462}{91530} &:= \frac{87-46+2}{9+1+5+30} &:= \frac{8-(7-46) \times 2}{(9-1-5) \times 30} &:= \frac{8 \times (74+6 \times 2)}{(9+15) \times 30} &:= \frac{8^{7-4}+6-2}{9+1+530} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{2548}{106379} &:= \frac{(2+5-4) \times 8}{10^{6-3}-7+9} &:= \frac{2^5-4+8}{1 \times 06^3 \times 7-9} &:= \frac{2 \times 54-8}{(10+6)^3+79} &:= \frac{(2-5+4) \times 8}{1^{06}+37 \times 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{3472}{105896} &:= \frac{3-4+7-2}{10+58+9 \times 6} &:= \frac{3+4+7-2}{1 \times 05 \times 8 \times 9+6} &:= \frac{3+4-7+2}{-1 \times 05+8 \times 9-6} &:= \frac{34-7 \times 2}{10+5 \times 8 \times (9+6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{3572}{108946} &:= \frac{(3+5-7) \times 2}{10 \times 8-9-4-6} &:= \frac{3-5+7 \times 2}{(1+089) \times 4+6} &:= \frac{(3 \times 5-7) \times 2}{(10-8)^9-4 \times 6} &:= \frac{3 \times (5+7) \times 2}{(10+89 \times 4) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{3852}{104967} &:= \frac{3+8-5-2}{1 \times 04+(9+6) \times 7} &:= \frac{38-5 \times 2}{(10+4) \times 9 \times 6+7} &:= \frac{(3+8+5) \times 2}{1+(04+9) \times 67} &:= \frac{3+8+5^2}{10+4+967} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{3927}{105468} &:= \frac{3+9+2-7}{1-05+4 \times 6 \times 8} &:= \frac{3-9+27}{10+546+8} &:= \frac{(3 \times 9+2) \times 7}{10 \times 546-8} &:= \frac{3 \times (9-2)-7}{(1^{05}+46) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6840}{123975} &:= \frac{6 \times 8-40}{1-2 \times (3-9) \times (7+5)} &:= \frac{6 \times (8-4)+0}{(1+2+(3+9) \times 7) \times 5} &:= \frac{68-4+0}{(1 \times 239-7) \times 5} &:= \frac{(6+8) \times 4+0}{(1 \times 2+3 \times 9) \times 7 \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7428}{109563} &:= \frac{(7-4-2) \times 8}{1-09 \times (5-6 \times 3)} &:= \frac{7 \times 4-2 \times 8}{1 \times 09+56 \times 3} &:= \frac{(7-4+2) \times 8}{(1+09) \times (56+3)} &:= \frac{7 \times 4^2+8}{10 \times (9+56 \times 3)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7938}{105462} &:= \frac{7+9 \times 3+8}{(1 \times 05+4) \times 62} &:= \frac{79-3+8}{1054+62} &:= \frac{7 \times (9-3+8)}{(1+05 \times 4) \times 62} &:= \frac{7 \times (9+3+8)}{(10+5 \times 4) \times 62} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{8945}{103762} &:= \frac{(8-9+4) \times 5}{10 \times 3 \times 7-6^2} &:= \frac{8 \times (9-4)-5}{10 \times 37+6^2} &:= \frac{(8+9-4) \times 5}{(1+0376) \times 2} &:= \frac{89-4+5}{10^3+7 \times 6+2}
 \end{aligned}$$

• **Four Digit's Numerator**

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{3402}{185976} &:= \frac{3+4 \times 0 \times 2}{1 \times 85 \times (9-7)-6} &:= \frac{3 \times 4^{02}}{(1+8 \times 5) \times (9-7)^6} &:= \frac{3 \times (4-02)}{1-8-5 \times (9-76)} &:= \frac{3+4+02}{(1+8 \times 5) \times (9-7) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4068}{271539} &:= \frac{4+0 \times 6+8}{(2 \times 71-53) \times 9} &:= \frac{4+0 \times 68}{2^{7+1}+5-3+9} &:= \frac{4 \times (-06+8)}{2-7+1 \times 539} &:= \frac{4 \times 06 \times 8}{2 \times (715-3) \times 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4170}{293568} &:= \frac{(4+1) \times 7+0}{2 \times (93-5) \times (6+8)} &:= \frac{(4-1) \times 70}{(2+9) \times 3 \times 56 \times 8} &:= \frac{4-1+7+0}{2 \times (9+3+5 \times 68)} &:= \frac{4+1^7+0}{(2+9+3 \times (5+6)) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4072}{316598} &:= \frac{4+0 \times 72}{316-5 \times (9-8)} &:= \frac{4 \times (0 \times 7+2)}{3+1+6 \times (5+98)} &:= \frac{4 \times 072}{(316-5) \times 9 \times 8} &:= \frac{40 \times (7-2)}{(3-1) \times (6^5-9+8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4172}{380695} &:= \frac{((4+1) \times 72)}{(3^8+0 \times 6+9) \times 5} &:= \frac{4-1+7+2}{(((38 \times (0+6))-9) \times 5)} &:= \frac{4 \times 1 \times (7-2)}{(380-6-9) \times 5} &:= \frac{4 \times 1^{72}}{3 \times 8 \times (06+9)+5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4176}{258390} &:= \frac{4-(1-7) \times 6}{25 \times (8+3) \times 9+0} &:= \frac{4 \times (1+7+6)}{(2+5+8)^3+90} &:= \frac{4 \times (1+7-6)}{2+583-90} &:= \frac{4^{1+7-6}}{2 \times 5 \times (8+3) \times 9+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4275}{186390} &:= \frac{(4 \times 2-7) \times 5}{1-8+6^3+9+0} &:= \frac{(4-2+7) \times 5}{(18+6^3) \times 9+0} &:= \frac{4 \times 2+7+5}{1 \times 863+9+0} &:= \frac{(4+2+7) \times 5}{(1 \times 8+6)^3+90}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4698}{137025} &:= \frac{(4 \times 6 - 9) \times 8}{(1 - 3 + 702) \times 5} &:= \frac{4 - 6 + 98}{(1 + 3) \times 70 \times 2 \times 5} &:= \frac{4 \times 6 \times (9 - 8)}{1 \times 3 + 702 - 5} &:= \frac{4 \times (6 + 9 \times 8)}{13 \times 70 \times 2 \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4830}{219765} &:= \frac{4 \times 8 - 30}{2 - 1 + 9 + 76 + 5} &:= \frac{4 \times (8 - 3) + 0}{2 \times 1 \times (97 - 6) \times 5} &:= \frac{4 \times (8 + 3) + 0}{(21 \times 9 - 7) \times (6 + 5)} &:= \frac{4 + 8 + 30}{21 + 9 \times 7 \times 6 \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5164}{203978} &:= \frac{5 - 1^{64}}{20 + 3 + 9 \times (7 + 8)} &:= \frac{5 - 1 - 6 + 4}{2 \times 039 - 7 + 8} &:= \frac{5 + 1 + 6 + 4}{(2^{03} \times 9 + 7) \times 8} &:= \frac{5 + 1 + 6 - 4}{20 \times 3 + (9 - 7)^8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5427}{186930} &:= \frac{5 + 42 + 7}{(1 - 8 + 69) \times 30} &:= \frac{54 \times 27}{186 \times 9 \times 30} &:= \frac{54 + 27}{(1 + 8 - 6) \times 930} &:= \frac{54 - 27}{1^{86} \times 930} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5673}{419802} &:= \frac{(5 + 6) \times 7 - 3}{(4 - 1 - 9 + 80)^2} &:= \frac{5 - 6 + 7 - 3}{(4 - 1) \times (9 \times 8 + 02)} &:= \frac{5 + (6 - 7) \times 3}{4 + 1 \times 9 \times 8 \times 02} &:= \frac{5 + 6 - 7 - 3}{4 + 1 - 9 + 80 - 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6237}{198450} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 + 3 \times 7}{(1 \times 9 + 8 + 4) \times 50} &:= \frac{6 + 23 - 7}{(1 + 9 + 8 - 4) \times 50} &:= \frac{62 - 3 + 7}{(1 + 9 + 8 \times 4) \times 50} &:= \frac{623 - 7}{1 \times 98 \times 4 \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6435}{120978} &:= \frac{(6 + 4) \times (3 + 5)}{(1 + 20 \times 9 + 7) \times 8} &:= \frac{6 - (4 - 3)^5}{1 \times 2 \times (-09 + 7 \times 8)} &:= \frac{6 - 4 + 3 + 5}{((1 + 20) \times 9) + 7 - 8} &:= \frac{6 \times (4 - 3) \times 5}{12 \times (-09 + 7 \times 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6480}{197235} &:= \frac{6 \times 4 + 8 + 0}{1 \times 972 - 3 + 5} &:= \frac{(6 + 4) \times 8 + 0}{((1 + 9) \times 7^2 - 3) \times 5} &:= \frac{(6 - 4) \times 8 + 0}{1^{97} + 2 \times 3^5} &:= \frac{(6 - 4)^8 + 0}{1 \times 9 + 7 + (2 \times 3)^5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6498}{250173} &:= \frac{(6 + 4) \times 9 + 8}{(2 \times 5 + 01) \times 7^3} &:= \frac{6 - 4 \times (9 - 8)}{2 \times 5 \times (01 + 7) - 3} &:= \frac{6 \times (4 - 9 + 8)}{(2^5 + 01) \times 7 \times 3} &:= \frac{6 + (4 \times (9 \times 8))}{(2^5 + 01) \times 7^3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6831}{279450} &:= \frac{6 \times 8 \times 3 - 1}{(2 + 7) \times (9 + 4) \times 50} &:= \frac{6 \times 8 - 3 - 1}{(2 - 7 + 9) \times 450} &:= \frac{6 + 8 - 3 \times 1}{2 + 7 - 9 + 450} &:= \frac{6 + 83 - 1}{(2 + 7 + 9) \times 4 \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6840}{123975} &:= \frac{6 \times 8 - 40}{1 - 2 \times (3 - 9) \times (7 + 5)} &:= \frac{(6 + 8) \times 4 + 0}{(1 \times 2 + 3 \times 9) \times 7 \times 5} &:= \frac{6 \times (8 - 4) + 0}{(1 + 2 + (3 + 9) \times 7) \times 5} &:= \frac{68 - 4 + 0}{(1 \times 239 - 7) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6840}{329175} &:= \frac{6 \times 8 - 40}{(3 + 2 + 9 \times (1 + 7)) \times 5} &:= \frac{(6 + 8) \times 4 + 0}{(3 \times 2 \times 91 - 7) \times 5} &:= \frac{6 \times (8 - 4) + 0}{3 \times (2 + 9 \times 1) \times 7 \times 5} &:= \frac{68 - 4 + 0}{(3 \times 29 + 1) \times 7 \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6938}{274051} &:= \frac{6 \times 9 - 38}{2 \times (7 \times (40 + 5) + 1)} &:= \frac{6 - 9 + 3 + 8}{2 + 7 \times (40 + 5) - 1} &:= \frac{6 - 9 - 3 + 8}{2 - 7 \times (40 - 51)} &:= \frac{6 + 9 - 3 - 8}{2 \times (7 \times 4 + 051)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6948}{130275} &:= \frac{(6 + 9) \times 4 - 8}{1 \times 30^2 + 75} &:= \frac{(6 - 9 + 4) \times 8}{(1 \times 3 + 027) \times 5} &:= \frac{(6 - 9) \times (4 - 8)}{1 \times 3 \times (0 \times 2 + 75)} &:= \frac{6 \times ((9 - 4) \times 8)}{1 \times 30 \times 2 \times 75} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7014}{293586} &:= \frac{7 + 014}{293 \times (5 - 8 + 6)} &:= \frac{7 \times (01 + 4)}{2 \times 9^3 + 5 + 8 - 6} &:= \frac{70 \times 1 \times 4}{2 + (9 + 3^5 \times 8) \times 6} &:= \frac{70 \times 1^4}{293 \times 5 \times (8 - 6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7038}{214659} &:= \frac{7 \times 0 \times 3 + 8}{(2 - 1 + 46) \times 5 + 9} &:= \frac{7 + 03 + 8}{21 \times 4 \times 6 + 5 \times 9} &:= \frac{7 + 03 - 8}{2 - 1 + 4 + 65 - 9} &:= \frac{7 - 03 + 8}{((2 + 1)^4 - 6) \times 5 - 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7104}{285936} &:= \frac{(7 - 1) \times 04}{2 \times 8 \times 5 \times (9 + 3) + 6} &:= \frac{7 + 1 + 04}{2 + 8 \times 59 + 3 + 6} &:= \frac{7 + 1^{04}}{2 - 8 \times (5 - 9 - 36)} &:= \frac{7 + 1 - 04}{2 - 8 + 5 + 9 \times 3 \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7128}{365904} &:= \frac{7 - 1^{28}}{(3 + 65 + 9) \times 04} &:= \frac{7 - 1 - 2 + 8}{(3 + 65) \times 9 + 04} &:= \frac{7 - 12 + 8}{3 + 65 + 90 - 4} &:= \frac{7 + 1^2 \times 8}{3^6 + 5 + 9 \times 04} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7154}{296380} &:= \frac{7 \times (1^5 + 4)}{2 \times 9^{6-3} - 8 + 0} &:= \frac{7 \times (1 + 5) \times 4}{29 \times (6 - 3) \times 80} &:= \frac{7 \times 1^{54}}{2 - 9 \times (6 - 38) + 0} &:= \frac{7 + 154}{2 \times (9 + 6)^3 - 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7182}{436905} &:= \frac{(7 + 1 \times 8) \times 2}{(-4 + 369) \times 05} &:= \frac{(7 + 1) \times (8 - 2)}{4 + 3^6 \times (9 - 05)} &:= \frac{7 - 1^{82}}{(4 + 36) \times 9 + 05} &:= \frac{7 + 1 + 8 \times 2}{(4 + 3 \times (6 + 90)) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7308}{129456} &:= \frac{7 + 3 \times 0 \times 8}{1 \times 2 \times (9 + 4) \times 5 - 6} &:= \frac{7 \times (3 + 0 \times 8)}{1 \times 2 \times (9 \times 4 \times 5 + 6)} &:= \frac{7 \times 3 \times 08}{(1 + (2 + 9) \times 45) \times 6} &:= \frac{(7 + 308)}{12 \times (9 + 456)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7326}{159840} &:= \frac{7 \times (3 + 2 + 6)}{15 \times (9 \times 8 + 40)} &:= \frac{7 + 3 + 2 \times 6}{(1 + 5 + 9) \times 8 \times 4 + 0} &:= \frac{7 + 32 - 6}{(1 + 59) \times (8 + 4) + 0} &:= \frac{73 + 26}{1 \times 5 \times 9 \times (8 + 40)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7350}{192864} &:= \frac{(7 + 3) \times 5 + 0}{1 + 9 - 2 + 8 + 6^4} &:= \frac{(7 + 3) \times 50}{(1 + 9) \times (2 \times 8 + 6^4)} &:= \frac{(7 - 3) \times 50}{(1 + 9^2) \times 8^{6-4}} &:= \frac{7 + 3^5 + 0}{(1 + 9^2) \times 8 \times (6 + 4)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$\blacktriangleright \frac{7514}{296803} := \frac{7-5+1 \times 4}{(2-9+6+80) \times 3}$	$:= \frac{7-5 \times (1-4)}{(2+9) \times 6+803}$	$:= \frac{7-5 \times 1^4}{2+9+68+0 \times 3}$	$:= \frac{7+5 \times 1^4}{2 \times ((9-6) \times 80-3)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{7536}{190284} := \frac{(7-5) \times 3+6}{19+0284}$	$:= \frac{7 \times (5-3)-6}{1 \times 90+28 \times 4}$	$:= \frac{7+5 \times 3-6}{(1+90+2+8) \times 4}$	$:= \frac{75+3-6}{1902-84}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{7614}{390852} := \frac{7-6+1+4}{3 \times 90+8 \times 5-2}$	$:= \frac{7-6+14}{3+9 \times 085+2}$	$:= \frac{7 \times (6+1-4)}{3 \times 9 \times 08 \times 5-2}$	$:= \frac{7+6-1 \times 4}{3 \times (9 \times 08+5) \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{7812}{394506} := \frac{7 \times 8 \times 1-2}{3 \times 9+450 \times 6}$	$:= \frac{7 \times (8+12)}{3+9^4+506}$	$:= \frac{7+81+2}{39+4506}$	$:= \frac{78 \times 1^2}{3945-06}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{7853}{416209} := \frac{7 \times 8-5 \times 3}{41 \times (62-09)}$	$:= \frac{7 \times 8-53}{(4-1) \times (62-09)}$	$:= \frac{7-8+5-3}{4 \times 16-2-09}$	$:= \frac{78+5 \times 3}{41 \times 6 \times 20+9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{8064}{137592} := \frac{8+06 \times 4}{(1 \times 3+75) \times (9-2)}$	$:= \frac{8 \times (06-4)}{(1+3+7 \times 5) \times (9-2)}$	$:= \frac{8^{06-4}}{13 \times 7 \times (5+9-2)}$	$:= \frac{80 \times 6 \times 4}{((1+3)^7+5-9) \times 2}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{8190}{372645} := \frac{8-1+9+0}{3+72 \times (6+4)+5}$	$:= \frac{8 \times 1^{90}}{(3+7^2) \times (6-4+5)}$	$:= \frac{8+1+9+0}{37 \times (26-4)+5}$	$:= \frac{8+190}{(3^7+2^6) \times 4+5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{8310}{245976} := \frac{(8+3) \times 10}{2 \times 4 \times (59 \times 7-6)}$	$:= \frac{8-3 \times 1+0}{(2-4+5^{9-7}) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{8-3+10}{(2+4+5+9 \times 7) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{8+3-1+0}{2+(4 \times (5+9)-7) \times 6}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{8316}{459270} := \frac{8^3+16}{45 \times 9 \times (2+70)}$	$:= \frac{(8+3 \times 1) \times 6}{45 \times (9+2+70)}$	$:= \frac{(8+3) \times 16}{(45-9) \times 270}$	$:= \frac{83-1+6}{4 \times 5 \times 9 \times 27+0}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{8415}{270963} := \frac{(8-4-1) \times 5}{(2+70+9) \times 6-3}$	$:= \frac{8 \times (4+1)+5}{(2 \times 7+09) \times 63}$	$:= \frac{8-4+1^5}{2 \times (70+9)+6-3}$	$:= \frac{84+1+5}{2 \times 7 \times (-09+6^3)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{8612}{437059} := \frac{(8+6 \times 1) \times 2}{4 \times (3+70 \times 5)+9}$	$:= \frac{8 \times 6 \times 1 \times 2}{(4+3) \times (705-9)}$	$:= \frac{8+6 \times 1 \times 2}{4^{3+7-05}-9}$	$:= \frac{86+1 \times 2}{4^3 \times 70-5-9}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{87462}{91530} := \frac{87^{-4}+6-2}{9+1+530}$	$:= \frac{8-(7-46) \times 2}{(9-1-5) \times 30}$	$:= \frac{8 \times (74+6 \times 2)}{(9+15) \times 30}$	$:= \frac{87-46+2}{9+1+5+30}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{8790}{136245} := \frac{8-7+9+0}{(1-3 \times (6-2^4)) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{8 \times 7 \times 9+0}{1 \times 36+(2+4)^5}$	$:= \frac{8+7-9+0}{1 \times 3-(6-24) \times 5}$	$:= \frac{8+7+9+0}{1+362+4+5}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{8975}{136420} := \frac{(8-9+7) \times 5}{1 \times 36+420}$	$:= \frac{(8+97) \times 5}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 420}$	$:= \frac{8+9-7-5}{13 \times 6-4+2+0}$	$:= \frac{8+97-5}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 4 \times 20}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{9018}{327654} := \frac{9+01+8}{3+2 \times (7+6)+5^4}$	$:= \frac{9+0 \times 18}{3 \times (27-6) \times 5+4}$	$:= \frac{9+018}{327+654}$	$:= \frac{9 \times (-01+8)}{3 \times (2+765-4)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{9045}{168237} := \frac{9 \times 0 \times 4+5}{1-6+(8+2 \times 3) \times 7}$	$:= \frac{9 \times (0 \times 4+5)}{1+6+823+7}$	$:= \frac{9-04+5}{1 \times 6 \times (8+2+3 \times 7)}$	$:= \frac{90-4 \times 5}{1 \times 6 \times (8+23) \times 7}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{9152}{307648} := \frac{(9+1) \times 52}{(3^{07}-6+4) \times 8}$	$:= \frac{9 \times (15-2)}{3 \times (07+6^4+8)}$	$:= \frac{9+15 \times 2}{30-7+6^4-8}$	$:= \frac{9+15+2}{(30-7) \times (6+4 \times 8)}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{9207}{346518} := \frac{(9+2) \times 07}{(3+4) \times (6+51 \times 8)}$	$:= \frac{9+2+0 \times 7}{3 \times (4 \times 6 \times 5+18)}$	$:= \frac{9+20-7}{3 \times 46 \times (5+1^8)}$	$:= \frac{92+07}{3 \times (4+65) \times 18}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{9218}{435760} := \frac{(9+2 \times 1) \times 8}{4^3 \times 5 \times (7+6)+0}$	$:= \frac{9 \times (2+1+8)}{(43+5 \times 7) \times 60}$	$:= \frac{9+(2+1) \times 8}{(4+3 \times 5+7) \times 60}$	$:= \frac{9+21-8}{4 \times 35 \times 7+60}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{9285}{146703} := \frac{(9^2+8) \times 5}{1+(4+6) \times 703}$	$:= \frac{9 \times 2-8-5}{146-70+3}$	$:= \frac{9-2+8+5}{1 \times 4 \times (6+70+3)}$	$:= \frac{9 \times (2+8-5)}{14-6+703}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{9618}{357240} := \frac{9-6+18}{(35-7)^2-4+0}$	$:= \frac{9 \times (6+1 \times 8)}{(3+57 \times 2) \times 40}$	$:= \frac{9+6-1 \times 8}{3^5-7+24+0}$	$:= \frac{9+6-1^8}{(3+5+7-2) \times 40}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{9648}{271350} := \frac{9 \times 6 \times 4+8}{(2^7+1-3) \times 50}$	$:= \frac{9 \times 6 \times 4-8}{(2+7) \times 13 \times 50}$	$:= \frac{9 \times (6-4) \times 8}{27 \times 1 \times 3 \times 50}$	$:= \frac{96-4 \times 8}{2 \times (7-1) \times 3 \times 50}$
$\blacktriangleright \frac{9702}{153846} := \frac{9 \times 7+0 \times 2}{1+5^3 \times 8+4-6}$	$:= \frac{9 \times 7 \times 02}{(1-5^3 \times 8) \times (4-6)}$	$:= \frac{9+7-02}{1+5+3 \times (8+4) \times 6}$	$:= \frac{9+70-2}{15 \times 3^{8-4}+6}$

3.4 5 Equivalent Blocks

• Five Digit's Numerator

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10329}{68547} &:= \frac{1+03-2+9}{(6+8)\times 5-4+7} := \frac{1+03+29}{6^{8-5}-4+7} := \frac{1+03\times 2\times 9}{6\times (8+54)-7} \\
 &:= \frac{10\times 3^2+9}{685-4\times 7} := \frac{103+2\times 9}{(68+5)\times (4+7)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10423}{96785} &:= \frac{1-0+(4-2)\times 3}{(9-6)\times 7-8)\times 5} := \frac{1+04^2-3}{(9-6+7)\times (8+5)} := \frac{1+04\times (2+3)}{(9\times 6-7-8)\times 5} \\
 &:= \frac{1+04^2\times 3}{9\times (6\times 7+8)+5} := \frac{1\times 042\times 3}{(9-6)\times 78\times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10452}{73968} &:= \frac{1^{04}+5^2}{7-3\times (9-68)} := \frac{1+04^{5-2}}{(7+3)\times (9\times 6-8)} := \frac{1+04\times (5-2)}{7-3+96-8} \\
 &:= \frac{1+045\times 2}{(7+39)\times (6+8)} := \frac{104\times (5-2)}{(7+39)\times 6\times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10584}{79632} &:= \frac{1-0+5\times (8-4)}{(7+9+63)\times 2} := \frac{1-0+58+4}{79\times 6\times (3-2)} := \frac{10\times (5+8)-4}{79\times (6+3\times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(10\times 5-8)\times 4}{79\times (6\times 3-2)} := \frac{105+84}{79\times ((6+3)\times 2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10672}{49358} &:= \frac{-1\times 06+7\times 2}{4\times (9-3)+5+8} := \frac{1-0+6+7+2}{4+9+3+58} := \frac{1\times 06\times 7-2}{(4-9)\times (3-5\times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1^{06}+7)^2}{4\times 9\times (3+5)+8} := \frac{10+6+72}{49+358} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10692}{83754} &:= \frac{1-06+9+2}{8-3\times (7-5\times 4)} := \frac{-1\times 06+9\times 2}{(8+3+7)\times 5+4} := \frac{1-0+6+9+2}{(8+3\times 7)\times 5-4} \\
 &:= \frac{1\times 06+9\times 2}{8\times 3\times 7+5\times 4} := \frac{1\times 06\times 9\times 2}{837+5+4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10845}{67239} &:= \frac{1-0+8-4+5}{6+7\times (2-3+9)} := \frac{10+(8-4)\times 5}{6\times (7+2\times (3+9))} := \frac{1+084+5}{(6+7\times 2^3)\times 9} \\
 &:= \frac{1\times 0\times 84+5}{6-7+23+9} := \frac{10+845}{(6\times 7)^2\times 3+9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12360}{84975} &:= \frac{1-2+3+6+0}{8+49-7+5} := \frac{(1^2+3)\times 6+0}{8\times (4+9+7)+5} := \frac{(1-2+3)^6+0}{8+4\times 9\times (7+5)} \\
 &:= \frac{1\times 2\times 36+0}{(8+(4+9)\times 7)\times 5} := \frac{1\times 2^3\times 60}{(8+4\times 9)\times 75} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12830}{79546} &:= \frac{1^2\times (8-3)+0}{7+9+5+4+6} := \frac{1\times 2\times (8-3)+0}{7\times (9-5+4)+6} := \frac{1-2\times 8+30}{79+5\times 4-6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{12 \times (8-3) + 0}{(7 \times 9 - 5 + 4) \times 6} := \frac{(1-2+8) \times 30}{7 \times (9 \times 5 \times 4 + 6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13806}{59472} & := \frac{13 \times (8-06)}{59+4+7^2} := \frac{13+8 \times 0 \times 6}{5 \times (9+4) - 7 - 2} := \frac{13 \times (8+06)}{(5+9) \times 4 \times 7 \times 2} \\
 & := \frac{1+3 \times 80+6}{(5+9) \times (4+72)} := \frac{13+806}{(5 \times 9+4) \times 72} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13956}{80247} & := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 9 - 5 - 6}{8^{0^2} + 4 \times 7} := \frac{(1+3) \times (9+5-6)}{8 \times (02^4 + 7)} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times (9+5) - 6}{80 \times 2 + 47} \\
 & := \frac{1-3 \times 9+5 \times 6}{8 \times (-02+4) + 7} := \frac{139-5+6}{802-4+7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14308}{59276} & := \frac{1 \times 4+3+0 \times 8}{5+9+2+7+6} := \frac{14+3 \times 0 \times 8}{5+9+2+7 \times 6} := \frac{1-4 \times (3-08)}{5+9^2+7-6} \\
 & := \frac{1-4+30+8}{5 \times (9+2 \times 7+6)} := \frac{1 \times 4+30+8}{5 \times (9+27) - 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14529}{38076} & := \frac{1-4+5 \times 2 \times 9}{38 \times (0 \times 7+6)} := \frac{145-29}{380-76} := \frac{1^4 \times 5 \times 29}{380 \times (7-6)} \\
 & := \frac{145+29}{(3+80-7) \times 6} := \frac{(1+4 \times 5) \times 29}{38 \times 07 \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15093}{24768} & := \frac{1+50+9+3}{2 \times 4 \times (7-6) \times 8} := \frac{1+50+9 \times 3}{2^4 \times (7-6) \times 8} := \frac{150+9-3}{2^{4+7-6} \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{1+50+9^3}{2 \times (4+76) \times 8} := \frac{1+509-3}{2 \times 4 \times (7+6) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15093}{27864} & := \frac{1-(5-09) \times 3}{2 \times 7 \times (8-6) - 4} := \frac{1+50-9-3}{2+7 \times (8+6-4)} := \frac{1+50+9 \times 3}{2+78+64} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times 50+93}{((2+7) \times 8-6) \times 4} := \frac{150+9-3}{278+6+4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15280}{94736} & := \frac{15-2-8+0}{9+4 \times (7-3) + 6} := \frac{1 \times 5+2+8+0}{9-4 \times 7 \times (3-6)} := \frac{(1+5) \times 2+8+0}{(9+4) \times (7+3) - 6} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times 5 \times 2+80}{(9+4 \times 7 \times 3) \times 6} := \frac{1+52-8+0}{9 \times (4+7 \times 3+6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{24786} & := \frac{15-3+09}{(2-4+7) \times 8-6} := \frac{15+3 \times 09}{2-(4-7-8) \times 6} := \frac{1+53+09}{(2^4-7+8) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times 5 \times (30-9)}{2 \times (4+78) + 6} := \frac{1+5^3+0 \times 9}{2 \times (4+7 \times (8+6))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{48762} & := \frac{1+5+30-9}{4+8+76-2} := \frac{1+53+0 \times 9}{4+(8+76) \times 2} := \frac{(15-3) \times 09}{4 \times (8+76+2)} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times 5 \times 3 \times 09}{4-8+7 \times 62} := \frac{(15+3) \times 09}{4+8^{7-6+2}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15728}{90436} &:= \frac{1 \times 5 - 7 - 2 + 8}{9 - 04 + 3 \times 6} &:= \frac{1 \times 5 - 7 + 2 + 8}{9 + 043 - 6} &:= \frac{1 + 5 + 7 \times 2 - 8}{9 \times (04 + 3) + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + 5 - 7 \times (2 - 8)}{(90 + 4) \times 3 - 6} &:= \frac{(1 + 5) \times 7 \times 2 \times 8}{90 \times 43 - 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15873}{49062} &:= \frac{1 - 5 \times (8 - 7 - 3)}{4 + (9 + 06) \times 2} &:= \frac{1^{58} + 7 \times 3}{4 \times (9 + 06 + 2)} &:= \frac{(1 - 5 + 8 + 7) \times 3}{4 + 90 + 6 + 2} \\
 &:= \frac{1^5 + 8 + 7^3}{(4 + 90 \times 6) \times 2} &:= \frac{1 + 58 + 73}{4 \times (90 + 6 \times 2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15876}{30429} &:= \frac{1 \times 5 + 8 - 7 + 6}{(3 + 04) \times 2 + 9} &:= \frac{1 + 5 \times (8 - 7 + 6)}{30 \times (4 - 2) + 9} &:= \frac{(1^{58} + 7) \times 6}{3^{04} + 2 + 9} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + 58 + 7 + 6}{30 \times 4 + 2 \times 9} &:= \frac{(1 - 5 + 8) \times 7 \times 6}{304 + 2 \times 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16038}{45927} &:= \frac{1 \times 60 - 38}{4 + 5 \times 9 + 2 \times 7} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 + 038}{45 + 9 \times (2 + 7)} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times (03 + 8)}{(4 + 5 + 9 \times 2) \times 7} \\
 &:= \frac{16 \times (03 + 8)}{4 \times (5 + 9) \times (2 + 7)} &:= \frac{160 + 38}{(4 + 59) \times (2 + 7)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16932}{54780} &:= \frac{1 + 6 + 9 + 3 - 2}{54 - 7 + 8 + 0} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times (9 - 3) - 2}{54 + 7 \times 8 + 0} &:= \frac{1 + (6 + 9) \times 3^2}{5 \times (4 + 7) \times 8 + 0} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + 6 + 9 \times 3) \times 2}{5 \times 4 \times 7 + 80} &:= \frac{1 + 6 \times (9 + 3 + 2)}{5 \times (47 + 8) + 0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17094}{52836} &:= \frac{1 \times 7 + 0 \times 9 + 4}{52 - 8 \times 3 + 6} &:= \frac{17 + 09 - 4}{5 \times (2 + 8) + 3 \times 6} &:= \frac{1 + 7 + 09 \times 4}{5 \times (2 + 8 \times 3) + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + 70 - 9 + 4}{(5 \times 2 + 8 \times 3) \times 6} &:= \frac{1 + 70 + 94}{528 - 3 \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17256}{40983} &:= \frac{1 + 7^{2+5-6}}{4 - 09 + 8 \times 3} &:= \frac{1 \times 7 - 2 + 5 + 6}{40 + 9 - 8 - 3} &:= \frac{1 - 7 - 2 + 56}{40 - 9 + 83} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + 72 + 5 - 6}{(40 + 9 + 8) \times 3} &:= \frac{1 + 7 + 2 \times 56}{4 \times 09 \times 8 - 3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17360}{52948} &:= \frac{17 - 3 + 6 + 0}{5 + (2 + 9 - 4) \times 8} &:= \frac{1 - 7 \times 3 + 60}{5 \times 2 \times (9 + 4) - 8} &:= \frac{1 + 73 + 6 + 0}{(5 + 2) \times 9 \times 4 - 8} \\
 &:= \frac{1^7 \times 3 \times 60}{5 + 2^9 + 4 \times 8} &:= \frac{(1 \times 7 - 3) \times 60}{(52 + 9) \times (4 + 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17896}{42503} &:= \frac{1 \times 78 - 9 \times 6}{42 + 5 \times 03} &:= \frac{1 - 7 + 8 + 9 \times 6}{4 \times 2 + 5^{03}} &:= \frac{1 - 7 - 8 + 9 \times 6}{42 + 50 + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + 78 - 9 - 6}{4 - 2 + 50 \times 3} &:= \frac{1 + 7 + 8 \times (9 + 6)}{4 + 2 \times 50 \times 3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18693}{54270} &:= \frac{1 + 8 \times (6 + 9) + 3}{5 \times (4 - 2 + 70)} &:= \frac{(1 - 8 + 69) \times 3}{5 \times 4 \times 27 + 0} &:= \frac{1 + 86 + 9 - 3}{(5 - 4) \times 270}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{186 \times 9 \times 3}{54 \times 270} & := \frac{18 \times 6 + 9^3}{(5+4) \times 270} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18792}{36540} & := \frac{1-8+7 \times 9-2}{(3-6) \times (5-40)} & := \frac{1+8+7+92}{3 \times (6 \times 5+40)} & := \frac{1-8+7+9 \times 2}{36-5+4+0} \\
 & := \frac{(1+8-7) \times 9^2}{3 \times (65+40)} & := \frac{(1+8+7) \times 9 \times 2}{(3+6+5) \times 40} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18942}{70356} & := \frac{18+9-4-2}{70-3+5+6} & := \frac{1 \times 8-9+4 \times 2}{(7-03) \times 5+6} & := \frac{1^8+94 \times 2}{703+5-6} \\
 & := \frac{1+8-9+42}{(7 \times 03+5) \times 6} & := \frac{18 \times (9-4+2)}{(70+3+5) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19320}{74865} & := \frac{1 \times 9-3+2+0}{74-8 \times 6+5} & := \frac{1-9+32+0}{74+8+6+5} & := \frac{(1+9 \times 3) \times 2+0}{7+(48-6) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{(1-9) \times (3-20)}{74 \times 8-65} & := \frac{(1+9 \times 3)^2+0}{7 \times (4+86 \times 5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19437}{80256} & := \frac{(19+4) \times 3-7}{8 \times (02+5 \times 6)} & := \frac{1 \times 9+4 \times 3 \times 7}{(80-2) \times 5-6} & := \frac{(19+4 \times 3) \times 7}{8 \times 02 \times 56} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times 9+43 \times 7}{80 \times (2 \times 5+6)} & := \frac{(1-94) \times (3-7)}{8 \times 02^5 \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19572}{64308} & := \frac{1+9-5+7+2}{6 \times 4+30-8} & := \frac{(1 \times 9-5) \times 7 \times 2}{64 \times 3-08} & := \frac{(1^9+5) \times 7^2}{6+4 \times 30 \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{1+9 \times 5 \times (7+2)}{6^4+30+8} & := \frac{1-9 \times (5-7)+2}{64-3+08} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19703}{45628} & := \frac{1 \times 9+7+03}{4 \times (5+6-2)+8} & := \frac{1 \times 9+70-3}{4+5 \times 6^2-8} & := \frac{1^9 \times 703}{45 \times 6^2+8} \\
 & := \frac{1+9 \times 7 \times 03}{4 \times 5 \times (6+2 \times 8)} & := \frac{19 \times 7+0 \times 3}{4 \times 5+6^2 \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19720}{46835} & := \frac{1+9+7 \times 2+0}{4+68-3 \times 5} & := \frac{(1 \times 9+7) \times 2+0}{4-6+83-5} & := \frac{(1 \times 9-7) \times 20}{(4+6) \times 8+3 \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{(1+9 \times 7) \times 2+0}{4 \times (68+3+5)} & := \frac{(19-7) \times 20}{(46-8) \times 3 \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19734}{25806} & := \frac{1+(9-7)^3+4}{25-8+0 \times 6} & := \frac{1+9+(7-3) \times 4}{2^5+8-06} & := \frac{(1 \times 9+7-3) \times 4}{2 \times 5 \times 8-06} \\
 & := \frac{(19+7) \times 3 \times 4}{2+5 \times 80+6} & := \frac{1 \times 9+73-4}{(25-8) \times 06} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20137}{49568} & := \frac{2+01+3+7}{4+9+5+6+8} & := \frac{20+13-7}{4 \times (9+5-6+8)} & := \frac{2+01 \times 37}{(4+(9+(5-6))) \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{2+(-01+3)^7}{4 \times (9-5+6) \times 8} & := \frac{2 \times 013 \times 7}{4 \times 95+68}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20174}{95368} &:= \frac{2 \times 01 \times (7+4)}{(9-5+3+6) \times 8} := \frac{2+01+74}{9+5 \times (3+68)} := \frac{2^{01 \times 7} + 4}{(9 \times (5+3) + 6) \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{2+0174}{95+3^6+8} := \frac{20-(1-7) \times 4}{9-5+3 \times 68} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{21056}{97384} &:= \frac{2+1^{05} \times 6}{9-7+3+8 \times 4} := \frac{2+1 \times 05 \times 6}{(9+7+3) \times 8-4} := \frac{2-1) \times 056}{(97 \times 3-8 \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{2^{1^{05} \times 6}}{(9+73-8) \times 4} := \frac{2 \times (1+05) \times 6}{9+(73+8) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{21483}{97650} &:= \frac{2+1 \times 4+8-3}{(9+7-6) \times 5+0} := \frac{2-1+4+83}{(9-7+6) \times 50} := \frac{2+1+4 \times 8 \times 3}{9 \times (7-6) \times 50} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (1+4) \times (8+3)}{(9+7-6) \times 50} := \frac{2 \times (14+8) \times 3}{(9-7) \times 6 \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{21693}{80574} &:= \frac{2+1 \times 6+9-3}{8 \times (0 \times 5+7)-4} := \frac{2+1+6+9+3}{80-5+7-4} := \frac{2^{1 \times 6} + 9 - 3}{(8+057) \times 4} \\
 &:= \frac{(2-1+6) \times (9+3)}{8 \times (05 \times 7+4)} := \frac{2+16 \times (9-3)}{(8+05) \times 7 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{21879}{64350} &:= \frac{2-1+(8+7) \times 9}{(6-4)^3 \times 50} := \frac{2^{1+8} + 7 - 9}{(6+4) \times 3 \times 50} := \frac{(2-(1-8) \times 7) \times 9}{(6 \times 4+3) \times 50} \\
 &:= \frac{2+18 \times 7-9}{(6+4^3) \times 5+0} := \frac{21 \times (8+7)-9}{(6+4 \times 3) \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{21978}{53460} &:= \frac{2 \times (1+9) \times 7+8}{5 \times 3 \times 4 \times 6+0} := \frac{2 \times 19+7-8}{5 \times (3 \times 4+6)+0} := \frac{(21+9+7) \times 8}{(5+3+4) \times 60} \\
 &:= \frac{21+978}{5 \times 3^4 \times 6+0} := \frac{2 \times (1+9 \times 78)}{(53+4) \times 60} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23184}{95760} &:= \frac{23+184}{9 \times (5 \times 7+60)} := \frac{23 \times (1+8+4)}{95 \times (7+6)+0} := \frac{23 \times 1^{84}}{95 \times (7-6)+0} \\
 &:= \frac{23 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4}{(9-5) \times 760} := \frac{23 \times (1+8) \times 4}{9 \times 5 \times 76+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{24138}{75096} &:= \frac{2-4 \times (1+3-8)}{7 \times (5+09-6)} := \frac{2+4+1+38}{7 \times (5+09+6)} := \frac{24+138}{(75+09) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times ((4+1)^3-8)}{7 \times (50+9 \times 6)} := \frac{2+4^{13-8}}{7 \times (50 \times 9+6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{24786}{95013} &:= \frac{2-4+7 \times (8-6)}{9+50-13} := \frac{2 \times (4 \times (7+8)-6)}{9 \times (50-1-3)} := \frac{2 \times 4 \times (7+8)-6}{9 \times 50-13} \\
 &:= \frac{2+(4+7) \times (8-6)}{95-01 \times 3} := \frac{2 \times (4+7 \times (8-6))}{(9 \times 5+01) \times 3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{24831}{76095} &:= \frac{2^4 \times 8-3-1}{(7+60+9) \times 5} := \frac{248+31}{760+95} := \frac{2 \times (4+8+3)+1}{(7-6) \times 095}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{248 \times (3+1)}{760 \times (9-5)} & := \frac{(2-4+8)^3+1}{760-95} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25140}{38967} & := \frac{2 \times (5+1+4)+0}{(3-8+9) \times 6+7} & := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 1 \times 4+0}{3+8+9+6 \times 7} & := \frac{2^{5+1}-4+0}{3 \times (8 \times (9-6)+7)} \\
 & := \frac{25 \times 1 \times 4+0}{38+9 \times (6+7)} & := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 14+0}{3 \times 8 \times 9-6+7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25194}{38760} & := \frac{2 \times (5+19)+4}{38+7 \times 6+0} & := \frac{25+(1+9) \times 4}{3 \times 8+76+0} & := \frac{(2+5-1) \times (9+4)}{(3-8+7) \times 60} \\
 & := \frac{2+5 \times (19+4)}{3 \times (8-7) \times 60} & := \frac{2 \times (5+1) \times (9+4)}{(3+8-7) \times 60} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25410}{73689} & := \frac{2 \times (5+4+1)+0}{7+3 \times (6+8)+9} & := \frac{2 \times 5 \times (4-1)+0}{7-3-6+89} & := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 4 \times 1+0}{7 \times 3+6+89} \\
 & := \frac{2+5+4-1+0}{(7-36) \times (8-9)} & := \frac{2 \times (5+4) \times 10}{(7+3+6 \times 8) \times 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25467}{39180} & := \frac{2 \times (5+4-6)+7}{3+9+1 \times 8+0} & := \frac{2+5+4+67}{39+1+80} & := \frac{2 \times (5^4+6-7)}{3 \times (9-1) \times 80} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times 54 \times (6+7)}{3 \times 9 \times 1 \times 80} & := \frac{2 \times (5-4) \times (6+7)}{39+1^8+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25704}{81396} & := \frac{(2 \times 5-7) \times 04}{8-(1+3-9) \times 6} & := \frac{2+5+7+04}{(8-1^3) \times 9-6} & := \frac{25+7+04}{(8-1+3+9) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{(25-7) \times 04}{81 \times 3-9-6} & := \frac{2 \times (5 \times 7+04)}{(8-1)^3-96} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25974}{30186} & := \frac{25+9+7-4}{30-1+8+6} & := \frac{2+5+9 \times 7+4}{3 \times 0 \times 1+86} & := \frac{259-74}{301-86} \\
 & := \frac{25 \times 9-7+4}{3 \times 01 \times 86} & := \frac{(2+5 \times 9) \times 7+4}{301+86} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25974}{63180} & := \frac{25+9+7-4}{6+3+1+80} & := \frac{2 \times (5+9) \times 74}{63 \times 1 \times 80} & := \frac{25 \times 9-7+4}{(6-3) \times 180} \\
 & := \frac{(2+5) \times 9 \times 74}{63 \times 180} & := \frac{(2+5+9) \times 74}{6^{3-1} \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{26130}{97485} & := \frac{2-6+1 \times 30}{9+7-4+85} & := \frac{26 \times 1 \times 3+0}{(9+7 \times 4) \times 8-5} & := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 130}{97 \times (4+8) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 13+0}{97+485} & := \frac{2+6 \times 1 \times 30}{9 \times 74+8+5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{26580}{49173} & := \frac{(2-6) \times 5+80}{(4 \times 9+1^7) \times 3} & := \frac{(2+6) \times 5+80}{(4+(9+1) \times 7) \times 3} & := \frac{2-6 \times (5-8)+0}{4 \times (9+1^7)-3} \\
 & := \frac{2+6 \times 5+8+0}{4+91-7 \times 3} & := \frac{2+6 \times (5+8)+0}{491-7^3}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{26730}{98415} &:= \frac{26-7+3+0}{9 \times (8-4+1 \times 5)} := \frac{2+67-3+0}{9 \times (8+4+15)} := \frac{(2+6 \times 7) \times 3+0}{9 \times (8+41+5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(26+7) \times 30}{9^{8-4-1} \times 5} := \frac{2+6 \times 73+0}{9 \times (8+4) \times 15} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{27034}{59861} &:= \frac{2 \times 7+0 \times 34}{5 \times (9-8) \times 6+1} := \frac{2 \times (7+03+4)}{5+9+8 \times 6 \times 1} := \frac{2+(7+03) \times 4}{5 \times 9+8 \times 6 \times 1} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times 7 \times (0 \times 3+4)}{5+(9+8) \times (6+1)} := \frac{2^7+03 \times 4}{5 \times (9-8+61)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{27401}{39856} &:= \frac{2 \times 7-4+01}{3-9-8+5 \times 6} := \frac{2 \times (7+4 \times 01)}{3-9+8+5 \times 6} := \frac{2+74+01}{3+98+5+6} \\
 &:= \frac{2^7+4 \times 01}{(3-9+8)^5 \times 6} := \frac{2-7+401}{(3+98-5) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{28476}{53901} &:= \frac{2+8-(4-7) \times 6}{53+9 \times 0 \times 1} := \frac{2+8+4+7 \times 6}{5 \times 3+90+1} := \frac{2 \times (84+7 \times 6)}{53 \times 9 \times 01} \\
 &:= \frac{28+476}{53+901} := \frac{28 \times (4 \times 7+6)}{(5-3) \times 901} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29536}{70148} &:= \frac{2-9-5 \times (3-6)}{7+01 \times 4+8} := \frac{2-9+5+3 \times 6}{7-01+4 \times 8} := \frac{2-9-5+36}{70-1-4-8} \\
 &:= \frac{2^{9+5-3-6}}{70+14-8} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times (5-3+6)}{70 \times (1+4)-8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29754}{31806} &:= \frac{2+9-7+54}{31 \times (8-06)} := \frac{29 \times (7+5-4)}{31 \times 8+0 \times 6} := \frac{29 \times (7+5 \times 4)}{31+806} \\
 &:= \frac{29 \times (7 \times 5-4)}{31^{8-06}} := \frac{29 \times ((7+5) \times 4)}{31 \times 8 \times 06} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30162}{47985} &:= \frac{(3+01) \times 6-2}{47-9-8+5} := \frac{30+16-2}{(4-7+9+8) \times 5} := \frac{3+01+62}{4+7+9+85} \\
 &:= \frac{(30-1) \times 6+2}{(4 \times (7+9)-8) \times 5} := \frac{30+16^2}{(4+79+8) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30186}{42957} &:= \frac{(3+01) \times 8-6}{4 \times 2 \times 9-5 \times 7} := \frac{30 \times 18+6}{(4 \times 29-5) \times 7} := \frac{3+01+8 \times 6}{4 \times 2 \times 9-5+7} \\
 &:= \frac{30+1 \times 8 \times 6}{(4+2) \times 9+57} := \frac{(30+1+8) \times 6}{4+(2+9 \times 5) \times 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31569}{74280} &:= \frac{3-1-5 \times (6-9)}{(7-4+2) \times 8+0} := \frac{3-1-5+6 \times 9}{7 \times 4^2+8+0} := \frac{3+(1 \times 5+6) \times 9}{(7 \times 4+2) \times 8+0} \\
 &:= \frac{31 \times 5+6+9}{(7-4+2) \times 80} := \frac{(3+1+5 \times 6) \times 9}{(7+4-2) \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31590}{48672} &:= \frac{(3+15) \times 90}{4 \times 8 \times (6+72)} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5 \times 9+0}{4 \times (8+6 \times 7+2)} := \frac{3 \times 1^5 \times 90}{4 \times 86+72}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(3+1+5) \times 90}{48 \times (6+7) \times 2} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5 \times 90}{4 \times 8 \times (67-2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31850}{42679} & := \frac{(3+1 \times 8) \times 50}{4 \times 26 \times 7+9} := \frac{3 \times 18 \times 50}{(4+2) \times 67 \times 9} := \frac{3 \times 1^8 \times 50}{(4+26) \times 7-9} \\
 & := \frac{(3+1^8) \times 50}{42 \times 6+7+9} := \frac{(3-1+8) \times 5+0}{4 \times (26-7)-9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31975}{48602} & := \frac{3+1+9+7+5}{4 \times 8+6+0 \times 2} := \frac{(3+1^9 \times 7) \times 5}{(4 \times 8+6) \times 02} := \frac{(3+1+9+7) \times 5}{4 \times 8+60 \times 2} \\
 & := \frac{((3-1) \times 9+7) \times 5}{4 \times 8 \times 6-02} := \frac{3 \times 1^9 \times 75}{4 \times 86-02} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{32097}{86415} & := \frac{3 \times 2+0 \times 9+7}{(8-6+4+1) \times 5} := \frac{3 \times (2+09)-7}{8^{6-4}+1+5} := \frac{3-(2-09) \times 7}{(8+6) \times (4+1+5)} \\
 & := \frac{3+20+9+7}{86+4+15} := \frac{3 \times (2+09 \times 7)}{8 \times (64+1)+5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{32691}{48075} & := \frac{3-2+6+9+1}{(4+8-07) \times 5} := \frac{3+2 \times (6+9)+1}{48+07-5} := \frac{3-26+91}{4+8 \times (07+5)} \\
 & := \frac{32+6 \times 9-1}{(4 \times 8-07) \times 5} := \frac{3^2 \times (69-1)}{(4+8) \times 075} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{32760}{94185} & := \frac{3^2-7+6+0}{9 \times 4 \times 1-8-5} := \frac{3+27-6+0}{9+(4+1 \times 8) \times 5} := \frac{32 \times (7-6)+0}{94+1-8+5} \\
 & := \frac{(3^2-7)^6+0}{94+18 \times 5} := \frac{(3^2-7) \times 60}{9-4 \times (1-85)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{32841}{76095} & := \frac{3-2+8 \times (4+1)}{(7-6) \times 095} := \frac{3+284 \times 1}{760-95} := \frac{(3-2+8) \times 41}{760+95} \\
 & := \frac{(3+2+8) \times 41}{(7+6) \times 095} := \frac{328 \times 4 \times 1}{760 \times (9-5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{34615}{87290} & := \frac{3+4 \times (6-1^5)}{87-29+0} := \frac{34+6+1+5}{87+29+0} := \frac{(3+4 \times (6-1)) \times 5}{(8-7) \times 290} \\
 & := \frac{3 \times 46 \times 15}{(8 \times 7+2) \times 90} := \frac{(346-1) \times 5}{(8+7) \times 290} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{34826}{79150} & := \frac{3-4+8+26}{(7+9-1) \times 5+0} := \frac{(3+4) \times (8 \times 2+6)}{7 \times (9+1) \times 5+0} := \frac{348-2+6}{(7+9 \times 1) \times 50} \\
 & := \frac{348+26}{(7+9+1) \times 50} := \frac{3 \times 4 \times (82+6)}{(7+9) \times 150} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{36075}{98124} & := \frac{3+6 \times 07+5}{(9+8 \times 1) \times 2 \times 4} := \frac{360^{7-5}}{(9+8) \times 12^4} := \frac{3+6 \times (07+5)}{(9+8) \times (1+2) \times 4} \\
 & := \frac{36 \times 075}{9 \times (812+4)} := \frac{(3+6 \times 07) \times 5}{9 \times (8^{1 \times 2}+4)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{36720}{84915} &:= \frac{(3-6+7)^2+0}{(8-4)\times(9-1)+5} := \frac{(3+6+7)\times 2+0}{84-9-1^5} := \frac{(3-6+7)\times 20}{((8-4)\times 9+1)\times 5} \\
 &:= \frac{3\times 6\times 7+2+0}{8\times(4\times(9-1)+5)} := \frac{36+7\times 20}{8\times 49+15} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{36971}{84025} &:= \frac{3+6+9-7\times 1}{8\times 4-02-5} := \frac{3697-1}{840\times 2\times 5} := \frac{(3-6)\times 9+71}{(8-4)\times 025} \\
 &:= \frac{3\times(6+9+7\times 1)}{(8\times 4-02)\times 5} := \frac{36+97-1}{(8+4)\times 025} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{37296}{51408} &:= \frac{3\times(7+2\times(9+6))}{5+140+8} := \frac{37+296}{51+408} := \frac{37\times(2\times 9-6)}{51\times(4+08)} \\
 &:= \frac{3+7^2+96}{51\times 4+0\times 8} := \frac{3+7^2-9-6}{51+4\times 0\times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{38701}{95264} &:= \frac{3-8+70\times 1}{(9+5+26)\times 4} := \frac{(3+8)\times 7+01}{95\times 2+6-4} := \frac{3+87+01}{(9+5)\times(2\times 6+4)} \\
 &:= \frac{3\times 8\times 7+01}{(9-5)\times 26\times 4} := \frac{3\times(8+70\times 1)}{9\times(5\times 2\times 6+4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{38724}{69150} &:= \frac{3+8-7+24}{6\times 9+1-5+0} := \frac{3+8+7+24}{(6+9\times 1)\times 5+0} := \frac{(3-87)\times(2-4)}{6\times(9+1)\times 5+0} \\
 &:= \frac{3\times 8\times 7\times 2\times 4}{6\times(9-1)\times 50} := \frac{(387-2)\times 4}{(6\times 9+1)\times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{38964}{71052} &:= \frac{3\times 8-9+6-4}{7-1+05^2} := \frac{3+8\times(9+6)-4}{7+105\times 2} := \frac{3\times(8\times 9+6)+4}{7\times(10+52)} \\
 &:= \frac{389+6-4}{710+5-2} := \frac{3\times(89+6)+4}{7+10\times 52} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{39125}{87640} &:= \frac{(3+9-1\times 2)\times 5}{8\times 7\times(6-4)+0} := \frac{(3\times 9\times 1-2)\times 5}{(8-7+6)\times 40} := \frac{3\times(9+1^2)\times 5}{(8+76)\times 4+0} \\
 &:= \frac{3\times(9-1)\times 25}{8\times 7\times 6\times 4+0} := \frac{3\times(9+1)^2\times 5}{(8+76)\times 40} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{39420}{57816} &:= \frac{39-4-20}{5-7+8+16} := \frac{3\times(9-4)\times 2+0}{57-8+1-6} := \frac{3\times(9+4+2)+0}{5+7+(8+1)\times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{3\times(9-4+20)}{5\times(7+8+1+6)} := \frac{3\times(9-4)\times 20}{57\times 8-16} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{39712}{65408} &:= \frac{39+7-12}{(6+5-4)\times 08} := \frac{3+9\times 7\times 1+2}{6\times 5\times 4-08} := \frac{3\times(9+7+1)\times 2}{6\times(5\times 4+08)} \\
 &:= \frac{3\times(9\times 7-12)}{65\times 4-08} := \frac{39\times 7-1^2}{(6+5)\times 40+8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{39725}{46081} &:= \frac{(3+9-7)\times 2\times 5}{4+6\times(08+1)} := \frac{3+97+25}{4+60+81} := \frac{3\times(9\times 7+2)+5}{4\times 60-8\times 1}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{3 \times (97 - 2 + 5)}{4 \times (6 + 081)} \quad := \frac{(3 + 9) \times 7 \times 25}{4 \times (608 + 1)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{40629}{51837} & := \frac{(4 + 06) \times 2 + 9}{5 - 1 \times 8 \times (3 - 7)} \quad := \frac{4 \times (0 \times 6 + 29)}{(5 - 1^8) \times 37} \quad := \frac{4 \times 06 \times 29}{51 + 837} \\
 & := \frac{406 - 29}{(5 + 1 \times 8) \times 37} \quad := \frac{406 + 29}{518 + 37} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{40986}{52371} & := \frac{(4 - 09 + 8) \times 6}{5 + 2 \times (3 + 7 - 1)} \quad := \frac{4 \times 09 \times (8 - 6)}{(5 + 2^3) \times 7 + 1} \quad := \frac{4 - 0 \times 9 + 86}{5 \times (2 + 3 \times 7 \times 1)} \\
 & := \frac{4 \times 09^{8-6}}{(5 + 2)^3 + 71} \quad := \frac{40 \times 9 \times (8 - 6)}{5 \times 23 \times (7 + 1)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41097}{56238} & := \frac{4 - 1 + 09 + 7}{5 + 6 + 23 - 8} \quad := \frac{4 \times 10 - 9 + 7}{5 \times (6 + 2 \times 3) - 8} \quad := \frac{4 - 10 + 9 \times 7}{5 \times (6 + 2^3) + 8} \\
 & := \frac{4 \times (10 + 9) \times 7}{56 \times (2 + 3 + 8)} \quad := \frac{(4 + 10) \times 9 + 7}{(56 + 2) \times 3 + 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41328}{95760} & := \frac{(4 + 1 \times 3)^2 - 8}{95 \times (7 - 6) + 0} \quad := \frac{41 \times (3 - 2 + 8)}{9 \times (5 \times 7 + 60)} \quad := \frac{41 \times (3 + 2 + 8)}{95 \times (7 + 6) + 0} \\
 & := \frac{41 \times (32 - 8)}{(9 \times 5 - 7) \times 60} \quad := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 328}{(9 - 5) \times 760} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41392}{87560} & := \frac{4 + 1 + 3 \times (9 - 2)}{8 \times 7 + 5 - 6 + 0} \quad := \frac{41 + 39 - 2}{(8 + 7) \times (5 + 6) + 0} \quad := \frac{4 \times (1 + 3 + 9) \times 2}{8 \times 7 \times 5 - 60} \\
 & := \frac{(4 - 1) \times 39 \times 2}{87 \times 5 + 60} \quad := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 39 \times 2}{8 \times 75 + 60} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41580}{76923} & := \frac{(4 + 1^5) \times 8 + 0}{7 \times 6 + 9 + 23} \quad := \frac{4 + 1 - 5 + 80}{7 + 69 \times 2 + 3} \quad := \frac{(4 - 1) \times 5 \times 8 + 0}{(7 + 69 - 2) \times 3} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + 1) \times 5 \times 8 + 0}{7 \times 6 \times 9 - 2^3} \quad := \frac{(4 + 1 \times 5) \times 80}{7 - 6 + (9 + 2)^3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{43659}{71280} & := \frac{(4 + 3)^{6+5-9}}{(7 + 1 + 2) \times 8 + 0} \quad := \frac{(4 + 3) \times (65 - 9)}{(7 + 1^2) \times 80} \quad := \frac{(4 + 3) \times 6 \times (5 + 9)}{(7 - 1) \times 2 \times 80} \\
 & := \frac{(43 + 6) \times (5 + 9)}{7 \times 1 \times 2 \times 80} \quad := \frac{(4 + (3 + 6) \times 5) \times 9}{(7 + 1 \times 2) \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{45309}{78261} & := \frac{4 - 5 + 3 + 09}{7 + 8 - 2 + 6 \times 1} \quad := \frac{4 + (5 - 3) \times 09}{7 - 8 \times (2 - 6) - 1} \quad := \frac{45 - 3 - 09}{7 + (8 + 2) \times (6 - 1)} \\
 & := \frac{4 \times (5 - 3 + 09)}{7 + ((8^2) + (6 - 1))} \quad := \frac{4 - 5 + 309}{7 \times (82 - 6 \times 1)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{45927}{83106} & := \frac{(4 - 5 + 9 - 2) \times 7}{83 - 1 - 06} \quad := \frac{4 - 5 + 92 - 7}{8 \times (3 + 10 + 6)} \quad := \frac{45 + 9 \times (2 + 7)}{(8 + 3 \times 10) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + 5 + 9)^2 \times 7}{8 + (3 + 1)^{06}} \quad := \frac{(4 + 59) \times 27}{(8^3 + 1) \times 06}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{46793}{51280} &:= \frac{46+7+93}{(5-1-2) \times 80} &:= \frac{4+6 \times (7+9) \times 3}{(5-1^2) \times 80} &:= \frac{4+6 \times 7+9 \times 3}{5 \times 1 \times 2 \times 8+0} \\
 &:= \frac{(4+6+7 \times 9) \times 3}{(5-1 \times 2) \times 80} &:= \frac{4 \times (6+7 \times 93)}{(5+1)^2 \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{47960}{81532} &:= \frac{4 \times (7+9-6)+0}{81-5 \times 3+2} &:= \frac{47+9-6+0}{81-5+3^2} &:= \frac{4+7+9+60}{8+1+5^3+2} \\
 &:= \frac{(4+7-9) \times 60}{81+5^3-2} &:= \frac{4 \times (7+9)+6+0}{8 \times 15-3+2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{49160}{83572} &:= \frac{4+9+1+6+0}{(8-3+5+7) \times 2} &:= \frac{4 \times (9+1^6)+0}{(8-3+5) \times 7-2} &:= \frac{4 \times (9+16)+0}{8+3 \times (5+7^2)} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (9+1 \times 6)+0}{83+5+7 \times 2} &:= \frac{4 \times 91+6+0}{(8+3) \times 57+2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{49320}{56718} &:= \frac{4 \times (9+3-2)+0}{5+6 \times 7-1^8} &:= \frac{(4+9-3) \times 2+0}{5-(6-7) \times 18} &:= \frac{4 \times 9 \times (3+2)+0}{5 \times (6 \times 7+1)-8} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (9+3 \times 2)+0}{(5+6) \times 7 \times 1-8} &:= \frac{(4+9+3) \times 20}{(5+6 \times 7-1) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{49536}{81270} &:= \frac{(49+5 \times 3) \times 6}{(8+1^2) \times 70} &:= \frac{4^{(9-5-3) \times 6}}{8 \times 12 \times 70} &:= \frac{4^{9+5-3-6}}{8 \times (1+2) \times 70} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (9 \times 5+3) \times 6}{(8-1) \times 270} &:= \frac{4+(9+5) \times 3 \times 6}{(8-1 \times 2) \times 70} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{50371}{82964} &:= \frac{5 \times (0 \times 3+7)-1}{(8+2 \times (9-6)) \times 4} &:= \frac{5 \times (03+7)+1}{(8-2+9+6) \times 4} &:= \frac{50+3 \times (7-1)}{8 \times 2 \times (9-6+4)} \\
 &:= \frac{5^{03}-7+1}{8+2 \times 96-4} &:= \frac{5 \times (-03+71)}{8 \times ((2+9) \times 6+4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{50463}{71289} &:= \frac{(5-04) \times 63}{(7+1+2) \times 8+9} &:= \frac{5 \times (0 \times 4+63)}{(7-1 \times 2) \times 89} &:= \frac{504-63}{7 \times 1^2 \times 89} \\
 &:= \frac{(5+04) \times 63}{(7+1 \times 2) \times 89} &:= \frac{50 \times 4 \times 6-3}{(7+12) \times 89} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{50672}{91843} &:= \frac{5+06+7-2}{9+1 \times 8+4 \times 3} &:= \frac{5-06+7^2}{91+8-4 \times 3} &:= \frac{50+6 \times (7-2)}{9 \times (1+8)+4^3} \\
 &:= \frac{50+6+72}{(9-1) \times (8 \times 4-3)} &:= \frac{(5+067) \times 2}{9+1 \times 84 \times 3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{52710}{96384} &:= \frac{5 \times (2+7)-10}{(9 \times 6-38) \times 4} &:= \frac{5 \times (27+1)+0}{(9+6-3-8)^4} &:= \frac{5^2 \times 7 \times 1+0}{(9+63+8) \times 4} \\
 &:= \frac{5 \times 2^7-10}{96 \times 3 \times (8-4)} &:= \frac{(5-2) \times 7 \times 10}{(9+6-3) \times 8 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{56430}{97812} &:= \frac{5 \times 6 \times (4-3)+0}{9 \times 7-8-1-2} &:= \frac{56+4^3+0}{(97+8-1) \times 2} &:= \frac{5 \times (6 \times 4+3)+0}{9+(7+8 \times 1)^2}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{5+6+4^3+0}{(9+7 \times 8 \times 1) \times 2} := \frac{(5+6+4) \times 30}{(9+7 \times 8) \times 12} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{57216}{98340} & := \frac{5+7 \times (2+1)+6}{98-3-40} := \frac{(5+7)^2 \times 16}{9 \times (8+3) \times 40} := \frac{5 \times 7 \times 2 \times 1-6}{98+3 \times 4+0} \\
 & := \frac{(5+7) \times 2^{1 \times 6}}{(9+8 \times 3) \times 40} := \frac{(5+7)^2-16}{9 \times 8 \times 3+4+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{60258}{79431} & := \frac{6 \times (0 \times 2+5)-8}{7+9+4 \times 3+1} := \frac{6-02+5 \times 8}{7+9+43-1} := \frac{6+02+58}{7 \times (9+4)-3-1} \\
 & := \frac{60+2 \times 58}{7 \times (9 \times 4-3)+1} := \frac{(6+0 \times 2+5) \times 8}{7+9 \times 4 \times 3+1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{60813}{75492} & := \frac{60+(8+1) \times 3}{7+5+4+92} := \frac{(6+081) \times 3}{(7+5 \times 4-9)^2} := \frac{(608+1) \times 3}{7 \times (5+4+9)^2} \\
 & := \frac{608+1^3}{7 \times (5+49) \times 2} := \frac{60 \times 8+13}{(7+5) \times (49+2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{62375}{94810} & := \frac{(6-2^3+7) \times 5}{9 \times 4-8+10} := \frac{6+2+37+5}{94-8-10} := \frac{6+2 \times 37-5}{(9+4) \times 8+10} \\
 & := \frac{(6+2+37) \times 5}{9 \times (48-10)} := \frac{(6+2-3) \times 75}{(9+48) \times 10} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{63504}{91287} & := \frac{63+5-04}{9 \times (1+2+8)-7} := \frac{(6+3 \times 50) \times 4}{912-8-7} := \frac{6+3 \times (50-4)}{9 \times 1 \times (2 \times 8+7)} \\
 & := \frac{6+3 \times 50+4}{(9+1) \times (2 \times 8+7)} := \frac{(6+3-5) \times 04}{9+1-2+8+7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{65184}{93702} & := \frac{6-5-1+8 \times 4}{9+37+0 \times 2} := \frac{(6-5+1)^8 \times 4}{(9^3+7) \times 02} := \frac{(6-5+1) \times 8 \times 4}{9 \times (3+7)+02} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times (5+1^8) \times 4}{9 \times (3 \times 7+02)} := \frac{(6 \times (5+1)-8) \times 4}{93+70-2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{65873}{90142} & := \frac{6-5+8+7+3}{9+01+4^2} := \frac{(6 \times 5+8) \times (7-3)}{(90+14) \times 2} := \frac{(6+5+8) \times 7 \times 3}{(90+1) \times (4+2)} \\
 & := \frac{6+5 \times 87 \times 3}{(901-4) \times 2} := \frac{6 \times (5+8)-7 \times 3}{90-14+2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{68913}{72540} & := \frac{6-8 \times (9-13)}{7-2-5+40} := \frac{6+89 \times 1^3}{(7-2) \times 5 \times 4+0} := \frac{(6 \times 8+9 \times 1) \times 3}{(7+2) \times 5 \times 4+0} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times 89+1-3}{(7+2+5) \times 40} := \frac{(6+89) \times (1+3)}{(7-2+5) \times 40} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{69741}{83025} & := \frac{6+(9-7)^4-1}{(8-3+0 \times 2) \times 5} := \frac{6+9 \times (7-4+1)}{(8-3) \times 02 \times 5} := \frac{6 \times (9 \times (7-4)+1)}{8 \times (3+02) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times (9+74+1)}{8 \times 3 \times 025} := \frac{6+9 \times (7+4 \times 1)}{(8-3) \times 025}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{70425}{81693} &:= \frac{(7-04+2) \times 5}{8-1 \times 6+9 \times 3} &:= \frac{(7+04 \times 2) \times 5}{81-6+9+3} &:= \frac{70+(4+2) \times 5}{8 \times 16-9-3} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 \times 04+2) \times 5}{8+169-3} &:= \frac{7 \times (0 \times 4+25)}{8 \times (16+9)+3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{71950}{83462} &:= \frac{(7-1+9) \times 5+0}{83-4+6+2} &:= \frac{(7-1) \times 9 \times 50}{(83+4) \times 6^2} &:= \frac{(7-1+9) \times 50}{834+6^2} \\
 &:= \frac{(7-1^9) \times 50}{(83+4) \times (6-2)} &:= \frac{(7+1^9) \times 50}{8^3-4 \times 6 \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{72150}{83694} &:= \frac{(7-2 \times 1) \times 5+0}{8-3 \times (6-9-4)} &:= \frac{7^2+1+50}{8+(36-9) \times 4} &:= \frac{(7-2 \times 1) \times 50}{8-(3-6) \times 94} \\
 &:= \frac{(7+21) \times 50}{8 \times (3 \times 69-4)} &:= \frac{(7+2+1) \times 50}{8 \times (3+69)+4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{76239}{85104} &:= \frac{7 \times 6-2^3+9}{8 \times (5+1^{04})} &:= \frac{(7 \times 6-2) \times 3+9}{8 \times 5+104} &:= \frac{7 \times (6-2+39)}{(85-1) \times 04} \\
 &:= \frac{(7+6 \times 2 \times 3) \times 9}{8 \times (5 \times 10+4)} &:= \frac{7 \times 62+39}{8+5 \times 104} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{79143}{86025} &:= \frac{7+9+1 \times 4+3}{8+6 \times 02-5} &:= \frac{7+(9+1 \times 4) \times 3}{8+6 \times (02+5)} &:= \frac{7 \times (9+1)-4+3}{8+60+2+5} \\
 &:= \frac{79+1+4 \times 3}{(8+6 \times 02) \times 5} &:= \frac{7+91 \times 4-3}{8 \times (60-2 \times 5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{79453}{82016} &:= \frac{7+(9+4-5) \times 3}{8 \times (-2 \times 01+6)} &:= \frac{79-4 \times 5+3}{8^2+0 \times 16} &:= \frac{7+94-5-3}{8 \times 2 \times 01 \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{(79+45) \times 3}{8^2 \times 01 \times 6} &:= \frac{7 \times ((9+4) \times 5-3)}{(8+20) \times 16} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{80725}{93641} &:= \frac{(8-0 \times 7+2) \times 5}{93+6-41} &:= \frac{80+(7+2) \times 5}{(9-3) \times 6 \times 4+1} &:= \frac{8+07+2 \times 5}{9-3+6 \times 4-1} \\
 &:= \frac{(8+07) \times 25}{(93-6) \times (4+1)} &:= \frac{(8+07)^2 \times 5}{9 \times (36 \times 4+1)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{85176}{94302} &:= \frac{8 \times 5+1-7-6}{9 \times 4-3-02} &:= \frac{8 \times (5+1+7-6)}{94-30-2} &:= \frac{(8+5+1^7) \times 6}{94-3+02} \\
 &:= \frac{8 \times (5+17+6)}{(94+30) \times 2} &:= \frac{(8+5-1) \times 7 \times 6}{9 \times (4^3-02)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{86754}{91320} &:= \frac{86-(7+5) \times 4}{9-1+32+0} &:= \frac{8+67+5 \times 4}{(9+1^3)^2+0} &:= \frac{86-7+54}{(9+1-3) \times 20} \\
 &:= \frac{8 \times (6-7+5 \times 4)}{(9-1^3) \times 20} &:= \frac{(8 \times 6-7) \times 5+4}{(9-1+3) \times 20}
 \end{aligned}$$

• **Four Digit's Numerator**

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{2358}{109647} &:= \frac{2-3-5+8}{1 \times 096+4-7} &:= \frac{2+3-5+8}{10 \times 9+6 \times 47} &:= \frac{2 \times (3 \times 5-8)}{(1+096-4) \times 7} \\
 &:= \frac{23+5-8}{10 \times (96+4-7)} &:= \frac{23-5+8}{(10+9) \times 64-7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{3645}{127980} &:= \frac{(3+6) \times 4 \times 5}{1^2 \times 79 \times 80} &:= \frac{3 \times 6 \times 4 \times 5}{1 \times 2 \times 79 \times 80} &:= \frac{3+6+4+5}{1^2 \times 79 \times 8+0} \\
 &:= \frac{3+6+45}{(1+2) \times 79 \times 8+0} &:= \frac{36-4-5}{12 \times (7+9 \times 8)+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{3645}{289170} &:= \frac{(3-6) \times (4-5)}{2 \times (8+9 \times 1) \times 7+0} &:= \frac{3-6+4+5}{28 \times (9+1+7)+0} &:= \frac{3-6 \times (4-5)}{2+89 \times (1+7)+0} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times (6-4) \times 5}{2 \times (8+9 \times 1) \times 70} &:= \frac{3 \times (6+4-5)}{(2 \times 8-9) \times 170} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{3918}{260547} &:= \frac{3 \times 9+1+8}{(2 \times 6-05)^4-7} &:= \frac{3-9+1 \times 8}{2 \times (60+5)-4+7} &:= \frac{3-9+18}{(2 \times (60-5)+4) \times 7} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times (9-1^8)}{2 \times (60+54) \times 7} &:= \frac{3+9-1 \times 8}{260-5+4+7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{3975}{241680} &:= \frac{(3 \times 9-7) \times 5}{(2 \times 41-6) \times 80} &:= \frac{(3-9+7) \times 5}{(2^{4+1}+6) \times 8+0} &:= \frac{3 \times 9-7-5}{2 \times 416+80} \\
 &:= \frac{(3+9-7) \times 5}{(24+1-6) \times 80} &:= \frac{3+9-7+5}{(2 \times 41-6) \times 8+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{3978}{250614} &:= \frac{(3-9+7) \times 8}{2 \times 50 \times (6-1)+4} &:= \frac{3^{9-7}-8}{2 \times 5 \times 06-1+4} &:= \frac{(3+9-7) \times 8}{2506+14} \\
 &:= \frac{3-9 \times (7-8)}{(250-61) \times 4} &:= \frac{3 \times (9+7-8)}{(2-506) \times (1-4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4167}{320859} &:= \frac{4-1^6+7}{3+2+085 \times 9} &:= \frac{4-1+6-7}{3 \times 20+85+9} &:= \frac{4-1-6+7}{(3+20) \times (8+5)+9} \\
 &:= \frac{4+1 \times 6-7}{3 \times 2 \times 08 \times 5-9} &:= \frac{4+16+7}{3+2085-9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4380}{169725} &:= \frac{4 \times 3-8+0}{(1-6 \times (9-7 \times 2)) \times 5} &:= \frac{4 \times 3+8+0}{1+6 \times (97+2^5)} &:= \frac{4^3 \times 8+0}{1-6+(9 \times 7)^2 \times 5} \\
 &:= \frac{(4-3) \times 8+0}{1-6-(9-72) \times 5} &:= \frac{4+3 \times 8+0}{(1-(6-9) \times 72) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4380}{176295} &:= \frac{4 \times 3-8+0}{1+(7 \times 6-2) \times (9-5)} &:= \frac{4 \times 3+8+0}{1 \times ((76 \times 2+9) \times 5)} &:= \frac{(4-3) \times 8+0}{(1+7+6) \times (2 \times 9+5)} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (3+8)+0}{(1+76) \times (2 \times 9+5)} &:= \frac{4+3 \times 8+0}{17 \times 6 \times (2+9)+5}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4508}{167923} &:= \frac{4 \times 5 + 08}{16 \times (7 \times 9 + 2) + 3} &:= \frac{4 \times 5 - 08}{(1 + 67 + 9^2) \times 3} &:= \frac{(-4 + 5) \times 08}{1 + 6 \times 7 \times (9 - 2) + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + 5 \times 0 \times 8}{1 \times (67 + 9) \times 2 - 3} &:= \frac{4 \times 5 + 0 \times 8}{(1 + 67) \times (9 + 2) - 3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{45309}{78261} &:= \frac{4 - 5 + 3 + 09}{7 + 8 - 2 + 6 \times 1} &:= \frac{4 - 5 + 309}{7 \times (82 - 6 \times 1)} &:= \frac{4 \times (5 - 3 + 09)}{7 + 8^2 + 6 - 1} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + (5 - 3) \times 09}{7 - 8 \times (2 - 6) - 1} &:= \frac{45 - 3 - 09}{7 + (8 + 2) \times (6 - 1)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4608}{317952} &:= \frac{4 \times 6 + 08}{3 \times 1 \times (7 + 9^{5-2})} &:= \frac{4 \times 6 - 08}{3 \times (179 + 5) \times 2} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 0 \times 8}{3 \times 17 + 9 \times 5^2} \\
 &:= \frac{4 - 6 + 08}{3 \times (1 + 7 \times 9 + 5) \times 2} &:= \frac{4 + 6 - 08}{3 - 1 + (7 \times 9 + 5) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5076}{129438} &:= \frac{(50 - 7) \times 6}{129 \times (43 + 8)} &:= \frac{5 + 07 + 6}{12 + 9 + 438} &:= \frac{5 + 07 - 6}{1 - (2 - 9 - 4 \times 3) \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{5 - 07 + 6}{1 \times 2 \times (9 + 4 + 38)} &:= \frac{50 - 7 \times 6}{1 - 29 \times (4 - 3 - 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5184}{293760} &:= \frac{(5 + 1) \times (8 + 4)}{2 \times (9 \times 3 + 7) \times 60} &:= \frac{5 \times (1 + 8) \times 4}{2 \times 9^3 \times 7 - 6 + 0} &:= \frac{5 + 1 \times 8 - 4}{2^9 - 3 + 7 - 6 + 0} \\
 &:= \frac{5 + 1 + 8 + 4}{(2 \times (9 + 3) - 7) \times 60} &:= \frac{51 - 8 - 4}{29 + 3^7 - 6 + 0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5274}{369180} &:= \frac{(5^2 - 7) \times 4}{(3 + 6 \times (9 + 1)) \times 80} &:= \frac{(5 - 2) \times (7 - 4)}{3^6 - 91 - 8 + 0} &:= \frac{5 - (2 - (7 - 4))}{3 \times (6 \times (9 + 1) + 80)} \\
 &:= \frac{5 + (2 - (7 - 4))}{36 \times (9 - 1) - 8 + 0} &:= \frac{52 - (7 \times 4)}{3 \times (69 + 1) \times 8 + 0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5320}{147896} &:= \frac{5 \times 3 + 20}{(1 \times 4 + 7) \times 89 - 6} &:= \frac{(5 - 3) \times 20}{14 \times (7 + 8 \times 9) + 6} &:= \frac{5 \times 3 \times 2 + 0}{1 \times ((4 + ((7 + 8) \times 9)) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{5 \times (3 - 2) + 0}{1 + (4 - 7) \times (8 - 9 \times 6)} &:= \frac{5 + 3 + 2 + 0}{1 \times 4 \times 7 \times 8 + 9 \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5427}{138690} &:= \frac{(5 + 4)^2 \times 7}{(13 + 8) \times 690} &:= \frac{(5 + 4) \times 27}{(1^3 + 8) \times 690} &:= \frac{5 + 4 + 2 + 7}{1 + (3 + 8 \times 6) \times 9 + 0} \\
 &:= \frac{54 + 27}{138 \times (6 + 9) + 0} &:= \frac{54 - 27}{1^{38} \times 690} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5730}{296814} &:= \frac{5 \times 7 - 30}{29 \times 6 + 81 + 4} &:= \frac{(5 + 7) \times 30}{(2^9 + 6) \times (8 + 1) \times 4} &:= \frac{5 \times (7 - 3) + 0}{((2 + 9) \times 6 + 8) \times 14} \\
 &:= \frac{5 \times (7 + 3) + 0}{(2^9 + 6) \times (8 + 1 - 4)} &:= \frac{57 + 3 + 0}{2^9 \times 6 + (8 + 1) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5817}{260934} &:= \frac{(5 + 81) \times 7}{(2 \times (6 + 09))^3 + 4} &:= \frac{5 - 8 + 17}{(2^6 + 093) \times 4} &:= \frac{5 \times (8 - 1^7)}{2 \times (60 + 9^3 - 4)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{5+8+1+7}{2+6+0934} & := \frac{5+8+1-7}{2+6+09 \times 34} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5926}{180743} & := \frac{(5+9)^2+6}{1+80 \times (74+3)} & := \frac{5-9+2 \times 6}{1+80 \times (7-4)+3} & := \frac{5+9-2 \times 6}{1-(8-07 \times 4) \times 3} \\
 & := \frac{5+9-2-6}{(1+(8+07) \times 4) \times 3} & := \frac{5+9-2+6}{1+80 \times 7-4 \times 3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5943}{108672} & := \frac{5+9-4-3}{10-(8-67) \times 2} & := \frac{5+9 \times (4-3)}{1 \times (08-6)^7 \times 2} & := \frac{5 \times (9-4)+3}{1 \times (08-6)^{7+2}} \\
 & := \frac{(59+4) \times 3}{1 \times 08 \times 6 \times 72} & := \frac{(5+9) \times 4^3}{(1 \times 08-6)^{7 \times 2}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5967}{103428} & := \frac{5 \times 9-6 \times 7}{1-0+3+(4+2) \times 8} & := \frac{5-9+6+7}{(1+03^4) \times 2-8} & := \frac{5 \times (9-6) \times 7}{(10-3) \times (4+2^8)} \\
 & := \frac{5+9-6+7}{1+03+(4-2)^8} & := \frac{59-6+7}{(1+03) \times (4+2^8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5976}{418320} & := \frac{5 \times (9-7)-6}{(4-1+8+3) \times 20} & := \frac{(5+9-7) \times 6}{(41+8) \times 3 \times 20} & := \frac{5-9+7 \times 6}{(4+1) \times (8^3+20)} \\
 & := \frac{5+9-7-6}{(4 \times 1 \times 8+3) \times 2+0} & := \frac{5+97-6}{4 \times (1+83) \times 20} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6015}{437892} & := \frac{6 \times 01 \times 5}{4 \times 3 \times 7 \times (8+9 \times 2)} & := \frac{6 \times 015}{4 \times 3 \times 78 \times (9-2)} & := \frac{6-01^5}{4+378-9 \times 2} \\
 & := \frac{6-01+5}{(4-3+7) \times (89+2)} & := \frac{60-15}{(43-7) \times (89+2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6045}{178932} & := \frac{(6-04) \times 5}{1+7+8 \times (9-3)^2} & := \frac{60 \times 4+5}{1 \times 78 \times 93-2} & := \frac{6+04+5}{((17+8) \times 9-3) \times 2} \\
 & := \frac{6+04-5}{1-7 \times (8-9 \times 3-2)} & := \frac{60+4 \times 5}{(1+789) \times 3-2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6048}{371952} & := \frac{6 \times 0 \times 4+8}{3 \times (71+95-2)} & := \frac{(6-04) \times 8}{3-7+19 \times 52} & := \frac{6+04-8}{3 \times (7+1 \times 9+5^2)} \\
 & := \frac{6+0 \times 48}{3 \times (7 \times 19-5 \times 2)} & := \frac{60-48}{3+7-1+9^{5-2}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6174}{358092} & := \frac{(6+1) \times (7-4)}{3 \times 5 \times 80+9 \times 2} & := \frac{6-1+7 \times 4}{3 \times 58 \times (09+2)} & := \frac{6-1 \times 7+4}{(3-5+80+9) \times 2} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times (1+7 \times 4)}{3 \times 58^{0 \times 9+2}} & := \frac{6 \times 1^{74}}{3+(5 \times (80-(9+2)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6210}{439875} & := \frac{6 \times 21+0}{(4+3) \times (9+8) \times 75} & := \frac{6 \times (2-1)+0}{(4+3-9+87) \times 5} & := \frac{6^2 \times 1+0}{(43-9) \times (8+7) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{6^{2+1}+0}{4 \times 3 \times (9+8) \times 75} & := \frac{6+2+10}{((4+3 \times 9) \times 8+7) \times 5}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6273}{159408} &:= \frac{6^2 \times 7 + 3}{15 \times 9 \times (40 + 8)} &:= \frac{6 \times (2 + 7) - 3}{(15 - 9)^4 + 0 \times 8} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 + 73}{1 \times 5 \times 9 \times (40 + 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times (2 \times 7 + 3)}{(1 + 5) \times 9 \times (40 + 8)} &:= \frac{6 + 2 \times 7 - 3}{(1 \times 5 + 9 + 40) \times 8} & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6489}{231750} &:= \frac{(6 - 4) \times 8 - 9}{(2 + 3 \times 1^7) \times 50} &:= \frac{(64 - 8) \times 9}{(23 + 1) \times 750} &:= \frac{6 - (4 - 8) \times 9}{(2 + (3 + 1) \times 7) \times 50} \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times (4 + 8 + 9)}{2 \times 3 \times 1 \times 750} &:= \frac{6 + 4 \times 8 \times 9}{2 \times 3 \times 1750} & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6498}{152703} &:= \frac{6 - (4 - 9) \times 8}{1 + 5 \times (2 + 70) \times 3} &:= \frac{6 - 4 \times (9 - 8)}{1 \times 5 + 2 \times 7 \times 03} &:= \frac{6 \times (4 - 9 + 8)}{(1^5 + 2 \times 70) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times (4 + 9 - 8)}{1^5 \times (2 + 703)} &:= \frac{6 + 4 \times (9 - 8)}{1 \times 5^2 + 70 \times 3} & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6504}{198372} &:= \frac{(6 - 5) \times 04}{1 + (9 - 8 + 3 + 7)^2} &:= \frac{6 \times 5 + 04}{1 - (9 - 83) \times 7 \times 2} &:= \frac{6 + 5 \times 04}{1 - 9 \times 8 \times (3 - 7 \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times (5 - 04)}{198 - 3 \times (7 - 2)} &:= \frac{6 + 50 - 4}{(19 \times 83) + 7 + 2} & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6804}{375921} &:= \frac{6 \times 8 + 04}{3 + 7 \times 5 \times (9^2 + 1)} &:= \frac{(-6 + 8) \times 04}{(3 + (7 - 5) \times 9)^2 + 1} &:= \frac{6 \times 8 + 0 \times 4}{3^7 + 5 \times (92 + 1)} \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times (8 - 04)}{3 \times ((7 + 5 + 9)^2 + 1)} &:= \frac{68 + 0 \times 4}{3759 - 2 \times 1} & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6975}{128340} &:= \frac{(6 - 9 + 7) \times 5}{1 \times 28 + 340} &:= \frac{(6 + 9) \times (7 - 5)}{1^2 \times (8^3 + 40)} &:= \frac{6 \times (9 - 7) \times 5}{1 \times 2 \times (8^3 + 40)} \\
 &:= \frac{6 + 9 + 7 \times 5}{(1 + 2 \times (8 + 3)) \times 40} &:= \frac{6 + 9 + 75}{(1 + 2) \times (8^3 + 40)} & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7056}{123984} &:= \frac{7 + 0 \times 56}{1 - 2 + (39 - 8) \times 4} &:= \frac{7 + 056}{123 + 984} &:= \frac{7 \times 056}{(1 + 2 \times 3) \times 984} \\
 &:= \frac{70 \times 5 \times 6}{12 \times 3 + 9 \times 8^4} &:= \frac{70 - 56}{1 + 2 + 3^{9-8+4}} & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7056}{419328} &:= \frac{7 + 0 \times 56}{4 \times (1 + 93 + 2 + 8)} &:= \frac{7 + 056}{4 \times (1 + 9)^3 - 2^8} &:= \frac{7 \times 056}{4 \times (1 + 9^3 - 2) \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{70 + 56}{(4 + 1 \times 932) \times 8} &:= \frac{70 - 56}{4 \times (1 + 9 + 3) \times 2 \times 8} & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7128}{436590} &:= \frac{7 \times 12 - 8}{(43 + 6) \times (5 + 90)} &:= \frac{(7 + 1 \times 2) \times 8}{(4 + (3 + 6) \times 5) \times 90} &:= \frac{7 - 1 + 2 + 8}{(4^3 + 6) \times (5 + 9) + 0} \\
 &:= \frac{7 + 1^{28}}{4 + 36 + 5 \times 90} &:= \frac{7 + 1 + 28}{(43 + 6) \times 5 \times 9 + 0} & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7209}{146583} &:= \frac{(7 - 2) \times 09}{14 \times 65 + 8 - 3} &:= \frac{7 + 2 + 0 \times 9}{(1 - 4 + 6 + 58) \times 3} &:= \frac{7 + 2 + 09}{1^4 \times 6 \times (58 + 3)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{7+20+9}{(1 \times 4+6 \times 5 \times 8) \times 3} & := \frac{72+0 \times 9}{1 \times 4 \times 6 \times (58+3)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7290}{134865} & := \frac{7 \times 2+90}{(1+3) \times (486-5)} & := \frac{7^2-9+0}{(134+8+6) \times 5} & := \frac{7^2+9+0}{134 \times 8+6-5} \\
 & := \frac{7-2+9+0}{(13 \times 4-8) \times 6-5} & := \frac{7+2+9+0}{13 \times (4 \times 8-6)-5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7362}{408591} & := \frac{(7+3) \times (6+2)}{40 \times (8 \times (5+9)-1)} & := \frac{7-(3-(6-2))}{4 \times (08 \times (5+9)-1)} & := \frac{7+(3-(6+2))}{4 \times (0 \times 8+5)+91} \\
 & := \frac{7+(3-(6-2))}{(4 \times 08+5) \times 9 \times 1} & := \frac{7+(3+(6+2))}{408+591} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7406}{392518} & := \frac{7-4+0 \times 6}{3 \times ((9-2) \times 5+18)} & := \frac{7-4 \times 0 \times 6}{3+92 \times (5-1^8)} & := \frac{7-4+06}{3 \times 9+25 \times 18} \\
 & := \frac{7+4-06}{3 \times (9 \times 2 \times 5+1)-8} & := \frac{7+40-6}{3^{9-2}-5-1-8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7506}{392814} & := \frac{7+5-0 \times 6}{39 \times 2 \times 8 \times 1+4} & := \frac{7+5-06}{3 \times (92+8)+14} & := \frac{7+50-6}{3 \times (9+2) \times 81-4} \\
 & := \frac{75+0 \times 6}{3928+1-4} & := \frac{75-06}{3 \times 9+2^8 \times 14} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7695}{203148} & := \frac{(7-6+9) \times 5}{20 \times 3 \times (14+8)} & := \frac{7 \times (6+9)-5}{20 \times (31 \times 4+8)} & := \frac{(7+6-9) \times 5}{(2 \times 031+4) \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{7-6+9+5}{(2+031) \times (4+8)} & := \frac{7-6+9-5}{2 \times 03 \times (14+8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7851}{463209} & := \frac{(7+8) \times 5 \times 1}{4^6+320+9} & := \frac{7-8+5 \times 1}{4 \times 6+3+209} & := \frac{7-8+5-1}{4 \times 6-(3-20) \times 9} \\
 & := \frac{7+8-5-1}{(4 \times 6+3) \times 20-9} & := \frac{7+8+5 \times 1}{(4+6)^3+20 \times 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{8135}{240796} & := \frac{(8-1^3) \times 5}{240+796} & := \frac{(8+1 \times 3) \times 5}{2+(40 \times 7-9) \times 6} & := \frac{(8+1+3) \times 5}{240 \times 7+96} \\
 & := \frac{8-1+3+5}{2 \times (4 \times 07+9) \times 6} & := \frac{8-1+3-5}{2 \times (40+7)+9 \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{8205}{173946} & := \frac{(8-2) \times 05}{(1+7 \times 3 \times (9-4)) \times 6} & := \frac{8 \times 2 \times 05}{1+7 \times 3^{9-4}-6} & := \frac{8+2+0 \times 5}{1+7 \times (3 \times 9+4)-6} \\
 & := \frac{8+2+05}{(1+(7-3+9) \times 4) \times 6} & := \frac{8+2-05}{1-7 \times (3+9 \times (4-6))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{8325}{176490} & := \frac{(8-3) \times 2-5}{1+7 \times (6 \times 4-9)+0} & := \frac{(8-3 \times 2) \times 5}{176+4 \times 9+0} & := \frac{(83+2) \times 5}{1+7 \times (6^4-9)+0} \\
 & := \frac{8-3+2 \times 5}{17 \times 6 \times 4-90} & := \frac{8+32+5}{(17 \times 6+4) \times 9+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{8946}{172530} &:= \frac{8 \times 9 + 4 - 6}{(1 + 7^2 - 5) \times 30} &:= \frac{89 \times 4 - 6}{(1 + 7 \times 2^5) \times 30} &:= \frac{8 \times (9 + 4 - 6)}{1 \times 72 \times 5 \times 3 + 0} \\
 &:= \frac{8 + 9 - 4 - 6}{1 + 7 + 2 + 5^3 + 0} &:= \frac{89 - 4 + 6}{1725 + 30} & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{8952}{407316} &:= \frac{(8 - 9 + 5) \times 2}{4 \times (0 - (7 \times (3 - 16)))} &:= \frac{8 \times (9 - 5) - 2}{4 \times 07^3 - 1 - 6} &:= \frac{8 - 9 + 5 - 2}{4 \times 07 \times 3 + 1 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{8 \times (9 - 5 + 2)}{4 - 07 + 3^{1+6}} &:= \frac{8 + 9 - 5 - 2}{407 + 3 \times 16} & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9035}{218647} &:= \frac{9 \times 0 \times 3 + 5}{2 \times (1 - 8 + 64) + 7} &:= \frac{(9 - 03) \times 5}{(2 + 1^8)^6 + 4 - 7} &:= \frac{90 - 3 \times 5}{2^{1+8} + 6^4 + 7} \\
 &:= \frac{90 + 35}{2^{1+8} \times 6 - 47} &:= \frac{90 - 35}{(2 + 1 + 8)^{6+4-7}} & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9037}{165248} &:= \frac{(9 + 03) \times 7}{(1 + 6 + 5^2) \times 48} &:= \frac{9 \times 0 \times 3 + 7}{1 - 6 + 5 + 2^4 \times 8} &:= \frac{(9 - 03) \times 7}{1 \times 6 \times (5 \times 24 + 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{9 \times (0 \times 3 + 7)}{(1 + 6 + 5) \times 2 \times 48} &:= \frac{9 \times 03 \times 7}{16 \times (52 \times 4 + 8)} & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9165}{304278} &:= \frac{9 + 1^6 + 5}{30 + (4 + 2) \times 78} &:= \frac{9 + 1^6 - 5}{30 + (4 - 2)^7 + 8} &:= \frac{9 + 1 \times 6 + 5}{(304 \times 2) + (7 \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{9 + 1 \times (6 - 5)}{3 \times 04 \times 27 + 8} &:= \frac{9 + 1 + 6 \times 5}{304 + 2^7 \times 8} & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9168}{372450} &:= \frac{(9 - 1 - 6)^8}{(3 + 7^2) \times 4 \times 50} &:= \frac{(9 + 1 + 6) \times 8}{((3 + 7)^2 + 4) \times 50} &:= \frac{(9 + 1 - 6) \times 8}{(3 + 7 + 2^4) \times 50} \\
 &:= \frac{9 - 1^6 + 8}{(3 + 7 \times 2 - 4) \times 50} &:= \frac{9 \times 1 \times 6 \times 8}{(37 + 2) \times 450} & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9264}{105378} &:= \frac{9 \times 2 - 6 - 4}{1 + 05 \times (3 + 7 + 8)} &:= \frac{9 \times 2 - 6 + 4}{1 + 05^3 + 7 \times 8} &:= \frac{(9 \times 2 - 6) \times 4}{1 + 0537 + 8} \\
 &:= \frac{9^2 \times 64}{1053 \times 7 \times 8} &:= \frac{9 \times 2 \times 6 \times 4}{(10 + 53) \times 78} & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9270}{143685} &:= \frac{9^2 - 7 + 0}{1 \times ((4 \times (36 \times 8)) - 5)} &:= \frac{9 - 2 + 7 + 0}{1 \times 4 - 3 + 6^{8-5}} &:= \frac{9 + 2 - 7 + 0}{1 + 4 + 3 \times (6 + 8 + 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{9 + 2 + 7 + 0}{1 \times 4 \times (3 + 68) - 5} &:= \frac{92 - 70}{1 \times 4 - 3 + 68 \times 5} & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9387}{214560} &:= \frac{(9 \times 3 + 8) \times 7}{2 \times (1 + 4) \times 560} &:= \frac{(9 - 3 + 8) \times 7}{(2 - 1) \times 4 \times 560} &:= \frac{9 \times 3 + 8 + 7}{2^{1+4} \times 5 \times 6 + 0} \\
 &:= \frac{9 - 3 + 8 + 7}{(2 + 14) \times 5 \times 6 + 0} &:= \frac{9 - 3 + 8 - 7}{2 \times 1 \times (4 \times 5 + 60)} & \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9430}{287615} &:= \frac{9 \times 4 - 30}{2 \times (8 + 76) + 15} &:= \frac{9 - 4 + 3 + 0}{2 \times (87 + (6 + 1) \times 5)} &:= \frac{9 - 4 - 3 + 0}{2 + 87^{-6+1} - 5}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{9+4-3+0}{(2-8+7) \times 61 \times 5} & := \frac{9+4+3+0}{2+(87-6) \times (1+5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9576}{103824} & := \frac{(9 \times 5 - 7) \times 6}{1 \times 03 \times 824} & := \frac{9 \times (5+7) + 6}{103 \times (8 \times 2 - 4)} & := \frac{(9-5) \times 76}{(1+03) \times 824} \\
 & := \frac{95 \times (7-6)}{103 \times (8-2+4)} & := \frac{95-76}{10+3 \times 8^2+4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9576}{104832} & := \frac{(9+5) \times 76}{(10+4) \times 832} & := \frac{(9-5) \times 76}{1 \times 04 \times 832} & := \frac{9+5 \times 7-6}{(1+04+8) \times 32} \\
 & := \frac{95 \times (7-6)}{10 \times 4 \times (8 \times 3+2)} & := \frac{95-76}{104 \times (8-3 \times 2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9612}{358047} & := \frac{(9-6+1) \times 2}{3^5+8+047} & := \frac{9 \times 6 \times 1-2}{3^5 \times 8+0 \times 4-7} & := \frac{9-6+1^2}{3 \times (5+8) \times 04-7} \\
 & := \frac{9 \times (6-1 \times 2)}{3 \times (5 \times 80+47)}; & := \frac{9+6+1^2}{3+5+(80+4) \times 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9810}{426735} & := \frac{(9-8) \times 10}{4-2+6 \times 73-5} & := \frac{9-8+1+0}{4+2 \times (6+7) \times 3+5} & := \frac{9 \times (8+10)}{(42-6-7) \times 3^5} \\
 & := \frac{9+8-1+0}{4 \times (26 \times 7-3-5)} & := \frac{9+8+1+0}{4 \times 2 \times 6+735}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.5 6 Equivalent Blocks

• Five Digit's Numerator

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10374}{62985} & := \frac{1 \times 03+7+4}{6+2+9 \times 8+5} & := \frac{1+037+4}{(6 \times 2-9) \times 85} & := \frac{(10-3+7) \times 4}{(6-2) \times (9+8) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times 03 \times 7 \times 4}{(6-2+98) \times 5} & := \frac{(1+03) \times 7 \times 4}{(6+2+9) \times 8 \times 5} & := \frac{(10-3) \times 7 \times 4}{(6+29 \times 8) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10439}{76285} & := \frac{1^{04} \times 39}{(7-6) \times 285} & := \frac{1 \times 043+9}{(7 \times 6 \times 2-8) \times 5} & := \frac{1^{04}+3+9}{(7+6-2+8) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times 04 \times 39}{76 \times (2+8+5)} & := \frac{10 \times (43+9)}{76 \times (2+8) \times 5} & := \frac{10+4^3-9}{7+6^2 \times (8+5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10584}{37926} & := \frac{(1+05) \times (8-4)}{3+7 \times (9+2)+6} & := \frac{1 \times 05 \times 8-4}{3 \times (7-9 \times (2-6))} & := \frac{1 \times 05 \times (8+4)}{3 \times 7 \times 9+26} \\
 & := \frac{1^{05} \times 84}{3 \times 79+2^6} & := \frac{(1+05) \times (8+4)}{3 \times (7+9^2)-6} & := \frac{(1+05) \times 84}{3 \times 7 \times (92-6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10635}{97842} & := \frac{1+06+3-5}{9+7+8 \times 4-2} & := \frac{1+06+3+5}{(9+(7+8) \times 4) \times 2} & := \frac{(1+06-3) \times 5}{9+7+84 \times 2}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{10 + (6+3) \times 5}{9 \times 7 \times 8 + 4 - 2} & := \frac{10 \times (6-3+5)}{9 \times (78+4) - 2} & := \frac{10 \times (6+3) - 5}{97 \times 8 + 4 + 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10923}{45678} & := \frac{1 + (09-2) \times 3}{4 \times 5 - 6 + 78} & := \frac{1 + 09 + 23}{4 + 56 + 78} & := \frac{1 + 09 \times 2 \times 3}{(4+5 \times 6) \times 7 - 8} \\
 & := \frac{109 + 23}{(4+5 \times (6+7)) \times 8} & := \frac{10 + 9^2 \times 3}{4^5 + 6 \times 7 - 8} & := \frac{10 + 9^2 - 3}{(45 - 6 + 7) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10923}{48657} & := \frac{1 + 09 - 2 + 3}{(4-8+6+5) \times 7} & := \frac{1 + (09-2) \times 3}{(4+(8-6) \times 5) \times 7} & := \frac{1 + 09 + 23}{4 + 86 + 57} \\
 & := \frac{10 + 92 - 3}{4 + 86 \times 5 + 7} & := \frac{10 \times (9+2) \times 3}{(48-6) \times 5 \times 7} & := \frac{10 + 9^2 - 3}{4 \times (86+5+7)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10935}{24786} & := \frac{1^{09} \times 3 \times 5}{(2-4+7) \times 8 - 6} & := \frac{(1 \times 09 - 3) \times 5}{2-4+(7+8) \times 6} & := \frac{1 + 09 + 35}{(2^4 - 7 + 8) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{10 \times 9 - 3 \times 5}{2 \times (4+78) + 6} & := \frac{10 \times 9 + 3 \times 5}{(24-7) \times (8+6)} & := \frac{10 \times (9-3) \times 5}{2 \times (4+7 \times 8 \times 6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12397}{58604} & := \frac{1 \times 2 + 3^{9-7}}{58 - 6 + 0 \times 4} & := \frac{1 + 2 + 3 + 9 + 7}{5 \times 8 + 60 + 4} & := \frac{1 \times 2 - (3-9) \times 7}{(58-6) \times 04} \\
 & := \frac{1 + 2^3 \times 9 - 7}{(5+8) \times 6 \times 04} & := \frac{(1-2+3+9) \times 7}{(5+86) \times 04} & := \frac{1 + (-2+3 \times 9) \times 7}{(5+8) \times (60+4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12749}{53680} & := \frac{1 + 2 - 7 \times (4-9)}{(5+3-6) \times 80} & := \frac{(12+7) \times 4^9}{(5+3)^6 \times 80} & := \frac{(1+2 \times 7+4) \times 9}{5 \times 3 \times 6 \times 8 + 0} \\
 & := \frac{12 \times (7 \times 4 - 9)}{(5-3) \times 6 \times 80} & := \frac{1 + 274 - 9}{(5+3+6) \times 80} & := \frac{1 - 2 + 7 \times 49}{5 \times 36 \times 8 + 0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12789}{36540} & := \frac{1 + (2-7+8) \times 9}{(3-6+5) \times 40} & := \frac{1 + 2 \times (7+8+9)}{36 \times 5 - 40} & := \frac{1 \times 2^7 - 8 \times 9}{(3+6-5) \times 40} \\
 & := \frac{1 - 27 + 89}{3 \times (6+54) + 0} & := \frac{12 - 7 + 8 \times 9}{36 \times 5 + 40} & := \frac{(1-2+7+8) \times 9}{3 \times 6 \times 5 \times 4 + 0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12804}{39576} & := \frac{1 - 2 + 8 + 04}{3 - 9 \times 5 + 76} & := \frac{1 + 28 + 04}{3 \times (9-5) \times 7 + 6} & := \frac{(1+2+8) \times 04}{3 \times 9 \times 5 + 7 - 6} \\
 & := \frac{12 + 80 - 4}{3 \times 95 - 7 - 6} & := \frac{1 + 2 \times 80 + 4}{3 + 9 \times 57 - 6} & := \frac{128 + 04}{395 + 7 + 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13572}{96048} & := \frac{1 \times 3 + 5 + 7 - 2}{96 + 04 - 8} & := \frac{(1+3+5 \times 7) \times 2}{9 \times 60 + 4 + 8} & := \frac{1 + 3 \times 5 \times 7 - 2}{(96-04) \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times 3 + 57 \times 2}{9 \times (60+4 \times 8)} & := \frac{13 \times (5+7) \times 2}{(9+60) \times 4 \times 8} & := \frac{13 \times (57+2)}{9 \times 604 - 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13680}{24795} & := \frac{(1+3) \times 6 - 8 + 0}{2 \times 4 + 7 + 9 + 5} & := \frac{(1-3+6) \times 8 + 0}{2+4+7+9 \times 5} & := \frac{1^3 \times 6 \times 8 + 0}{(2+4) \times 7 + 9 \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{1^{36} \times 80}{(2-(4-7) \times 9) \times 5} & := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 6 \times 8 + 0}{247+9+5} & := \frac{(1+3) \times 6 \times 8 + 0}{(2+4) \times (7 \times 9 - 5)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13902}{45678} &:= \frac{1 \times 3 \times (9 - 02)}{(4 + 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8} &:= \frac{1 + 39 + 02}{4 + 56 + 78} &:= \frac{1 \times 3 + 9^{02}}{4 \times ((5 + 6) \times 7 - 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times 3 + 90 - 2}{4 + 5 \times (67 - 8)} &:= \frac{13 + 90 + 2}{4 + 5 + 6 \times 7 \times 8} &:= \frac{1 + 3 \times 9 + 0 \times 2}{4 \times 5 - 6 + 78} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14586}{39270} &:= \frac{1^4 + 5^{8-6}}{(3 + 9 - 2) \times 7 + 0} &:= \frac{1^4 \times (58 - 6)}{3 + 9 + 2^7 + 0} &:= \frac{1 + 4^{5-8+6}}{(3 \times 9 - 2) \times 7 + 0} \\
 &:= \frac{145 - 8 + 6}{392 - 7 + 0} &:= \frac{(1 + 4) \times (58 - 6)}{(3 + 9 - 2) \times 70} &:= \frac{1 \times 4 \times (5 + 86)}{(3 + 9 + 2) \times 70} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15480}{37926} &:= \frac{(1^5 + 4) \times 8 + 0}{(37 + 9) \times 2 + 6} &:= \frac{1 \times 5 \times (4 + 8) + 0}{3 \times (7 + (9 - 2) \times 6)} &:= \frac{1 \times 5 \times 4 + 80}{3 \times 79 + 2 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{15 \times (4 + 8) + 0}{3 \times 7 \times (9 + 2 \times 6)} &:= \frac{(1 + 5) \times 4 \times 80}{(37 - 9)^2 \times 6} &:= \frac{(1^5 + 4) \times 80}{(3 + 7) \times (92 + 6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15960}{24738} &:= \frac{1 \times 5 + 9 + 6 + 0}{(2 + 4 + 7) \times 3 - 8} &:= \frac{1 + 5 \times 9 - 6 + 0}{(2 - 4) \times (7 - 38)} &:= \frac{1 + 5 + 9 \times 6 + 0}{2^4 + 7 \times (3 + 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1^5 + 9) \times 60}{2 \times (473 - 8)} &:= \frac{1 + 59 + 60}{(2 + 4) \times (7 + 3 \times 8)} &:= \frac{1 \times 5 \times 96 + 0}{2 + 4 + 738} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16027}{49538} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 - 02 + 7}{(4 + 9) \times (5 - 3) + 8} &:= \frac{1 - 6 + 027}{4 + 9 + 5 \times (3 + 8)} &:= \frac{1 + 6^{02} + 7}{4 \times (9 - 5 \times (3 - 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + 6 \times (02 + 7)}{(49 + 5) \times 3 + 8} &:= \frac{1 + 60 - 2 + 7}{4 \times 9 \times 5 + 3 \times 8} &:= \frac{1 + 60 + 27}{(49 - 5 \times 3) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16497}{25380} &:= \frac{(1^6 + 4) \times 9 + 7}{2 - 5 + 3 + 80} &:= \frac{1 + 6 \times (4 - 9 + 7)}{2 \times (5 - 3 + 8) + 0} &:= \frac{1 - 6 + 4 \times 9 \times 7}{2 \times 5 \times 38 + 0} \\
 &:= \frac{(16 + 4 \times 9) \times 7}{(2 \times 5 - 3) \times 80} &:= \frac{1 + (6 - 4)^9 + 7}{(2 + 5 + 3) \times 80} &:= \frac{16 \times (4 + 9) \times 7}{(25 + 3) \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16548}{70329} &:= \frac{1 - 6 + 5 - 4 + 8}{7 + 03 - 2 + 9} &:= \frac{1 - 6 + 5 + 4 + 8}{7 \times 03 \times 2 + 9} &:= \frac{1 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 8}{70 + 3 + 29} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times 6 + 54 - 8}{70 \times 3 + 2 + 9} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 \times (5 \times 4 + 8)}{703 + 2 + 9} &:= \frac{(1 + 6 + 5 \times 4) \times 8}{(70 + 32) \times 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16758}{20349} &:= \frac{1 - (6 - 7) \times (5 + 8)}{2 - 03 \times (4 - 9)} &:= \frac{1 - 6 + 7 + 5 \times 8}{2 + 0 \times 3 + 49} &:= \frac{1 + 6 + 7 \times (5 + 8)}{2^{03+4} - 9} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + 67 + 58}{2 \times 03^4 - 9} &:= \frac{(1 + 6 + 7) \times (5 + 8)}{(20 - 3) \times (4 + 9)} &:= \frac{(1 + 67 - 5) \times 8}{2 \times 034 \times 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16907}{38425} &:= \frac{1 - 6 + 9 + 07}{3 + 8 + 4 + 2 \times 5} &:= \frac{1 \times 6 + 9 + 07}{(3 \times (8 - 4) - 2) \times 5} &:= \frac{1 + 69 + 07}{(3 + 8 - 4) \times 25} \\
 &:= \frac{169 + 07}{(38 + 42) \times 5} &:= \frac{(1 + 6 \times 9) \times 07}{(3 + 8 \times 4) \times 25} &:= \frac{1 + 69 \times 07}{(3 + 8) \times 4 \times 25} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17253}{40896} &:= \frac{(1 + 7 - 2) \times 5 - 3}{-4 \times 08 + 96} &:= \frac{(1 + 7 + 2 \times 5) \times 3}{4 \times 08 + 96} &:= \frac{(1 \times 7^2 + 5) \times 3}{4 \times (0 \times 8 + 96)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{1+725+3}{4 \times 08 \times 9 \times 6} & := \frac{(17+2+5)^3}{(4 \times 08)^{9-6}} & := \frac{1725+3}{4^{0 \times 89+6}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17658}{39240} & := \frac{1+7+(6-5)^8}{3+9+2 \times 4+0} & := \frac{1 \times 76-58}{(3+9-2) \times 4+0} & := \frac{1 \times 76-5 \times 8}{3+9^2-4+0} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times 7+6 \times 5+8}{(3 \times 9-2) \times 4+0} & := \frac{1 \times 7 \times (6-5+8)}{(3+9)^2-4+0} & := \frac{1+7+658}{(39-2) \times 40} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17963}{40825} & := \frac{17-9+6-3}{4+08 \times 2+5} & := \frac{17+9 \times (6-3)}{(4+08 \times 2) \times 5} & := \frac{1-7+9+63}{(4 \times 08-2) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times 7+9 \times (6+3)}{4 \times (08+2) \times 5} & := \frac{17+96-3}{(40+8+2) \times 5} & := \frac{((1+7) \times 9-6) \times 3}{40+82 \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18360}{49572} & := \frac{1^8+3+6+0}{4+9+5+7+2} & := \frac{(1 \times 8-3) \times 6+0}{(4 \times (9-5)-7)^2} & := \frac{1^8 \times 3 \times 60}{495-7-2} \\
 & := \frac{(1+8+3) \times 60}{4 \times 9 \times (5+7^2)} & := \frac{1^{83} \times 60}{(4+9+5) \times (7+2)} & := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 3 \times 60}{(49+5) \times 72} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18537}{46092} & := \frac{18+(5+3) \times 7}{(-4+6) \times 092} & := \frac{(1+8-5) \times 37}{460-92} & := \frac{185+37}{4 \times (60+9) \times 2} \\
 & := \frac{1^{85} \times 37}{(4+6) \times 09+2} & := \frac{1+85 \times (3+7)}{46^{0 \times 9+2}} & := \frac{18 \times 5 \times 37}{460 \times 9 \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18543}{60927} & := \frac{1+8+5 \times (4-3)}{60-9+2-7} & := \frac{1 \times 8+(5+4) \times 3}{6 \times 09 \times 2+7} & := \frac{1 \times 85-43}{6 \times (09+2 \times 7)} \\
 & := \frac{(1+8+54) \times 3}{(60+9) \times (2+7)} & := \frac{1+8+5-4-3}{(6+09) \times 2-7} & := \frac{(185+4) \times 3}{(60+9) \times 27} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19047}{62583} & := \frac{1+9+04-7}{6-2-5+8 \times 3} & := \frac{1+9+04+7}{6+2+58+3} & := \frac{1+9 \times (-04+7)}{6-2+5+83} \\
 & := \frac{(1+9-04) \times 7}{6 \times (2 \times (5+8)-3)} & := \frac{(1 \times 9+04) \times 7}{62 \times 5-8-3} & := \frac{(19+04) \times 7}{6 \times 2+5+8^3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19072}{34568} & := \frac{(1^9+07) \times 2}{3+4+5 \times 6-8} & := \frac{(1 \times 9+07) \times 2}{3 \times 4 \times 5+6-8} & := \frac{1-9+072}{3+45+68} \\
 & := \frac{(-1+9) \times 07 \times 2}{3 \times 45+68} & := \frac{(1+9 \times 07) \times 2}{(3-4+5 \times 6) \times 8} & := \frac{(1 \times 9+07)^2}{(3^4-5) \times 6+8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19584}{20736} & := \frac{1+9-5+8+4}{2+07+3+6} & := \frac{1+9 \times 5-8-4}{(2+07-3) \times 6} & := \frac{1 \times 9 \times (5+8+4)}{(2+07) \times 3 \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{1+9+5 \times 8 \times 4}{(20+7+3) \times 6} & := \frac{1+9 \times 5 \times 8-4}{2^{07} \times 3-6} & := \frac{1+9 \times 58+4}{(20+73) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19650}{48732} & := \frac{1^{96} \times 50}{4 \times (8+7 \times 3+2)} & := \frac{1+9 \times (6+5)+0}{4 \times (8 \times 7+3 \times 2)} & := \frac{(1 \times 9-6) \times 50}{4 \times (87+3 \times 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(1+9-6) \times 50}{487+3^2} & := \frac{(1+9 \times 6) \times 5+0}{4-8+7^3 \times 2} & := \frac{1^9 \times 6 \times 50}{4+8+732}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19872}{40365} &:= \frac{1-9+8 \times (7-2)}{(4+03+6) \times 5} &:= \frac{1-9+8 \times (7+2)}{40+3 \times 6 \times 5} &:= \frac{(1+9+8) \times 7+2}{4 \times (0 \times 3+65)} \\
 &:= \frac{(19 \times 8)+72}{(4+03) \times 65} &:= \frac{1-9+8 \times 7^2}{4 \times 03 \times 65} &:= \frac{(1+9-8)^7 \times 2}{40 \times (3 \times 6-5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{21408}{36795} &:= \frac{2^{1-4+08}}{(3+6-7+9) \times 5} &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 4 \times 08}{36+79-5} &:= \frac{2 \times 1^4 \times 08}{(3+6+79) \times 5} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times (40+8)}{3+67+95} &:= \frac{2^{1 \times 4} \times 08}{(3 \times 6+7) \times 9-5} &:= \frac{2 \times 140+8}{(3+6 \times (7+9)) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{21697}{53408} &:= \frac{2-1+6 \times (9-7)}{(5+3-4) \times 08} &:= \frac{2 \times (1+6 \times (9-7))}{(5-3) \times 4 \times 08} &:= \frac{2+1+6^{9-7}}{(5+3+4) \times 08} \\
 &:= \frac{(2+1) \times (6+9)+7}{(5-3)^4 \times 08} &:= \frac{2-1+6+97}{(5+3) \times 4 \times 08} &:= \frac{((2+16) \times 9)+7}{5+3+408} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{21870}{64395} &:= \frac{2+1+8+7+0}{6+43+9-5} &:= \frac{2+1+87+0}{(6+4) \times 3 \times 9-5} &:= \frac{21+87+0}{6 \times (4 \times (3+9)+5)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (1-8+70)}{6+(4^3+9) \times 5} &:= \frac{21+8+7+0}{64+3 \times (9+5)} &:= \frac{2-18+70}{6 \times 4+3 \times 9 \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23046}{79158} &:= \frac{2-3+04 \times 6}{7+9 \times 1^5 \times 8} &:= \frac{23+046}{79+158} &:= \frac{23^{-04+6}}{79 \times (15+8)} \\
 &:= \frac{230-46}{79 \times 1^5 \times 8} &:= \frac{2 \times 30 \times 46}{79 \times 15 \times 8} &:= \frac{(2+30) \times 46}{(7 \times 91-5) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{24037}{59168} &:= \frac{2+4+0 \times 3+7}{5+9 \times (1-6+8)} &:= \frac{2^4+03+7}{5-9+1 \times 68} &:= \frac{2+40+3+7}{59+1+68} \\
 &:= \frac{24 \times 03-7}{5 \times (9+1-6) \times 8} &:= \frac{2 \times 40 \times 3+7}{5-9 \times (1-68)} &:= \frac{(2+40-3) \times 7}{(5+9 \times 1) \times 6 \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{24063}{75891} &:= \frac{2^4+0 \times 6-3}{7 \times (5-8+9)-1} &:= \frac{2 \times (4+06+3)}{7-5+8 \times (9+1)} &:= \frac{2+40-6+3}{7+(5+8) \times 9-1} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (40-6)-3}{(7+5) \times (8+9)+1} &:= \frac{(2+4 \times 06) \times 3}{(7-5)^8-9-1} &:= \frac{2 \times 40+63}{7+5 \times 89-1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{24651}{38097} &:= \frac{2 \times (4+6-5)+1}{3 \times 8+0 \times 9-7} &:= \frac{2^{4+6-5}+1}{3 \times (80-9 \times 7)} &:= \frac{2+46-5+1}{3+8 \times 09-7} \\
 &:= \frac{2-4+6+51}{3+80+9-7} &:= \frac{2+46 \times 5-1}{3 \times (8+09) \times 7} &:= \frac{24 \times (65+1)}{3 \times (809+7)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25938}{47160} &:= \frac{2+5 \times (9+3-8)}{4+(7-1) \times 6+0} &:= \frac{2 \times 5 \times (9+3 \times 8)}{(4+7-1) \times 60} &:= \frac{25 \times 9 \times (3+8)}{(4+71) \times 60} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (5+9)-3+8}{(4+7-1) \times 6+0} &:= \frac{2^5 \times (9+3 \times 8)}{4 \times (7+1) \times 60} &:= \frac{(2 \times 59+3) \times 8}{(4+7) \times 160} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{27135}{94068} &:= \frac{2-7+1 \times 35}{(9+4+0 \times 6) \times 8} &:= \frac{2-7+13 \times 5}{9 \times 4 \times 06-8} &:= \frac{2 \times (7-1+3) \times 5}{9 \times 40-6 \times 8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(2+7 \times 1) \times 3 \times 5}{9 \times (4+06 \times 8)} := \frac{2 \times (7-1) \times 3 \times 5}{(9+4) \times 06 \times 8} := \frac{2 \times (7-1) + 3^5}{(9+4) \times 068} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{27693}{81450} & := \frac{2+76-9 \times 3}{(8-1-4) \times 50} := \frac{2+(7+6+9) \times 3}{8 \times (1+4) \times 5+0} := \frac{2 \times (7+6 \times 9) - 3}{(8-1^4) \times 50} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times (7 \times (6+9) - 3)}{(8+1 \times 4) \times 50} := \frac{2 \times 7+69 \times 3}{(8+1+4) \times 50} := \frac{27 \times (6 \times 9 - 3)}{(8+1) \times 450} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{27918}{63450} & := \frac{2-7+9-1+8}{(6+3-4) \times 5+0} := \frac{2+79-1+8}{(6+34) \times 5+0} := \frac{2+79+18}{6^3+4+5+0} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times (7 \times 9 \times 1 - 8)}{(6+3-4) \times 50} := \frac{279-1+8}{(6+3+4) \times 50} := \frac{(2 \times (7+9) + 1) \times 8}{(6-3) \times 4 \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{28576}{39104} & := \frac{2 \times (8-5) + 7+6}{3+9+10+4} := \frac{2+(8+5-7) \times 6}{3+9+10 \times 4} := \frac{(2 \times (8+5) - 7) \times 6}{39 \times 1 \times 04} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times 85+7-6}{39 \times (10-4)} := \frac{(28 \times 5 - 7) \times 6}{3 \times 91 \times 04} := \frac{(2+8+5) \times 76}{39 \times 10 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29058}{67134} & := \frac{2+9 \times (-05+8)}{67-1-3+4} := \frac{2 \times 9+05 \times 8}{67 \times (1-3+4)} := \frac{29+058}{67+134} \\
 & := \frac{290+58}{67 \times 1 \times 3 \times 4} := \frac{29 \times (0 \times 5+8)}{67 \times (1+3+4)} := \frac{29 \times (05+8)}{67 \times (1+3 \times 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29058}{73146} & := \frac{2+9 \times (-05+8)}{7-(3-14) \times 6} := \frac{2 \times 9+05 \times 8}{(7+31) \times 4-6} := \frac{(2+90-5) \times 8}{73 \times 1 \times 4 \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{29+058}{7 \times 31-4+6} := \frac{2 \times (90+5-8)}{73 \times 1^4 \times 6} := \frac{29 \times (0 \times 5+8)}{73 \times (14-6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30618}{49572} & := \frac{3 \times (06+1^8)}{4+(9-5) \times 7+2} := \frac{3 \times (06+1 \times 8)}{4+9+57-2} := \frac{3 \times (06+1) \times 8}{4 \times (9+57+2)} \\
 & := \frac{30 \times 6+1+8}{(49-5) \times 7-2} := \frac{30+6 \times (1+8)}{4 \times (9+5 \times (7-2))} := \frac{3 \times 06 \times (-1+8)}{(4+(9+5) \times 7) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31207}{96458} & := \frac{3-1+2+07}{96-4-58} := \frac{3+12+07}{9+6+45+8} := \frac{31+20-7}{((9-6) \times 4+5) \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{3+1+2^{07}}{(96-45) \times 8} := \frac{3+1 \times 20 \times 7}{9 \times (6+4) \times 5-8} := \frac{3-1+207}{9+645-8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31248}{97650} & := \frac{3-1+2+4+8}{(9+7-6) \times 5+0} := \frac{3 \times 12 \times 4-8}{(9+76) \times 5+0} := \frac{(3-1+2^4) \times 8}{9 \times (7-6) \times 50} \\
 & := \frac{(3+1+2^4) \times 8}{(9+7-6) \times 50} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 2 \times 4 \times 8}{(9-7) \times 6 \times 50} := \frac{(3-1^2)^4 \times 8}{(9-7+6) \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31904}{57826} & := \frac{3+1 \times 9+04}{5+(7+8) \times 2-6} := \frac{(3-1)^{9-04}}{5-7+(8+2) \times 6} := \frac{(3+1 \times 9) \times 04}{5+78-2+6} \\
 & := \frac{3-1+90+4}{(5 \times 7-8+2) \times 6} := \frac{(3+1^9)^{04}}{57 \times 8+2+6} := \frac{(-3+19) \times 04}{(5+7 \times 8) \times 2-6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31950}{47286} &:= \frac{3 \times (1+9) - 5 + 0}{47 - 2 \times 8 + 6} := \frac{(3-1^9) \times 50}{4 + 72 \times (8-6)} := \frac{(3+1+9) \times 50}{(4+7)^2 \times 8 - 6} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times 1^9 \times 50}{4 \times (7^2 + 8) - 6} := \frac{(3+1^9) \times 50}{4 \times (72 + 8 - 6)} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 950}{4 + 7^2 \times 86} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{34827}{91650} &:= \frac{34 + (8-2) \times 7}{(9+1-6) \times 50} := \frac{(3-4) \times (8-27)}{(9+1^6) \times 5 + 0} := \frac{3^4 + 8^2 + 7}{(9-1^6) \times 50} \\
 &:= \frac{3+4 \times (8-2) \times 7}{9 \times 1^6 \times 50} := \frac{3+4 \times 8^2 + 7}{(9-1+6) \times 50} := \frac{34+8 \times 2 + 7}{(9-1 \times 6) \times 50} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{35490}{81627} &:= \frac{(3-5) \times (4-9) + 0}{8+1 \times 6+2+7} := \frac{3 \times (5-4+9) + 0}{(8-1) \times 6+27} := \frac{35-4+9+0}{8+1 \times 6 \times 2 \times 7} \\
 &:= \frac{35 \times 4 - 90}{(8+1) \times 6 \times 2 + 7} := \frac{3 \times (5-4) \times 90}{(8+1) \times (62+7)} := \frac{3 \times (5+4) \times 90}{81 \times (62+7)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{35706}{42198} &:= \frac{3-5+7+06}{4-2+19-8} := \frac{35-7-06}{4+2 \times (19-8)} := \frac{3+57+06}{4+2+1 \times 9 \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times 5 + 7) \times 06}{4 \times 21 + 9 \times 8} := \frac{3+5 \times 7 + 06}{4 \times (2+19-8)} := \frac{3^5 + 70 + 6}{(42-1) \times 9 + 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{36912}{80745} &:= \frac{3+6+9-1 \times 2}{8+07+4 \times 5} := \frac{(3-6+91) \times 2}{(80-7+4) \times 5} := \frac{3 \times (69+1) - 2}{(80+7+4) \times 5} \\
 &:= \frac{(3+6 \times 9 - 1) \times 2}{80 \times (7-4) + 5} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times (9-1)^2}{8 \times 07 \times 45} := \frac{(3 \times (6+9+1))^2}{80 \times 7 \times (4+5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{38049}{65721} &:= \frac{3+8+0 \times 49}{6+5+7+2-1} := \frac{3 \times 8+0 \times 4+9}{65-7-2+1} := \frac{3-8+049}{6-5 \times (7-21)} \\
 &:= \frac{380+49}{6+5 \times 7 \times 21} := \frac{3 \times (8+04 \times 9)}{6 \times (5 \times 7 + 2 + 1)} := \frac{(3+8) \times 04 \times 9}{6 \times 57 \times 2 \times 1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{38410}{65297} &:= \frac{3 \times 8 - 4 - 10}{6 - 52 + 9 \times 7} := \frac{3 \times 8 - 4 \times 1 + 0}{6 - 5 \times (2 - 9) + 7} := \frac{(3-8) \times (4-10)}{6-52+97} \\
 &:= \frac{(3+8-4) \times 10}{6^{5-2} - 97} := \frac{3 \times 8 \times (4+1) + 0}{6-5+29 \times 7} := \frac{38 \times (4+1) + 0}{6 \times 5 \times (2+9) - 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{39204}{67518} &:= \frac{3+9+2+04}{6-7+(5-1) \times 8} := \frac{3+9+20+4}{67-5 \times 1^8} := \frac{3 \times 9 \times (20+4)}{(67-5) \times 18} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times (92+04)}{(67-5 \times 1) \times 8} := \frac{392+04}{675-1+8} := \frac{3 \times 9 \times 2^{04}}{(6 \times 7 + 51) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{39240}{76518} &:= \frac{3+9+2 \times 4+0}{7+6 \times (5-1)+8} := \frac{(3+9-2) \times 4+0}{7 \times (6+5-1)+8} := \frac{3+9^2-4+0}{(7+6) \times (5-1+8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times 9 - 2) \times 4 + 0}{7 \times (6 \times 5 - 1) - 8} := \frac{(3+9)^2 - 4 + 0}{7 \times (6 \times 5 + 1 + 8)} := \frac{3 \times 92 + 4 + 0}{7 \times 6 \times (5 + 1 \times 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{39280}{75614} &:= \frac{3+9+28+0}{7 \times (5+6 \times 1^4)} := \frac{39 \times 2 \times 80}{7+5 \times (6+1)^4} := \frac{(3+9) \times (2+8) + 0}{7-(5-61) \times 4}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(3+9-2) \times 80}{7 \times (56-1) \times 4} & := \frac{(3 \times 9 - 2) \times 8 + 0}{7 \times 5 \times (6+1+4)} & := \frac{392+8+0}{756+14} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{39540}{67218} & := \frac{(3-9) \times 5 + 40}{6-7+2 \times (1+8)} & := \frac{(3+9) \times 5 - 40}{6 \times 7 \times (2-1) - 8} & := \frac{3 \times (9+5-4) + 0}{6+(7-2) \times (1+8)} \\
 & := \frac{(3+9) \times 5 + 40}{(6+7)^2 + 1^8} & := \frac{39+5-4+0}{6 \times (7+2+1) + 8} & := \frac{(3-9) \times (5-40)}{6+7^{2+1} + 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41375}{92680} & := \frac{4-1-3+75}{(9+2 \times 6) \times 8+0} & := \frac{(4+1 \times 3 \times 7) \times 5}{(9+26) \times 8+0} & := \frac{(4+1-3) \times 75}{(9-2) \times 6 \times 8+0} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times 13 - 7) \times 5}{9 \times (2^6 - 8) + 0} & := \frac{(4+1) \times (3+7) \times 5}{92 \times 6 + 8 + 0} & := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 375}{(9-2) \times 6 \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41832}{50796} & := \frac{4+1+8+3-2}{5-(07-9) \times 6} & := \frac{4 \times 1 \times (8+3) - 2}{5 \times (0 \times 7 + 9) + 6} & := \frac{4-1+83-2}{(5+07) \times 9-6} \\
 & := \frac{4 \times (1+8 \times 3) - 2}{50+7 \times 9+6} & := \frac{4-(1-83) \times 2}{(50-7-9) \times 6} & := \frac{4+1+(8+3)^2}{50+7+96} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41975}{63802} & := \frac{(4+1 \times 9+7) \times 5}{6^3 - 8^{02}} & := \frac{(4+19+7) \times 5}{6 \times 38+0 \times 2} & := \frac{4 \times 1^9 \times 75}{6 \times 38 \times 02} \\
 & := \frac{4 \times (1+9) + 7 \times 5}{6 \times (3+8 \times 02)} & := \frac{4 \times (1+9) \times 75}{6 \times 380 \times 2} & := \frac{4 \times 19 \times 75}{6 \times 38^{02}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{46710}{52938} & := \frac{4-6+7+10}{5-2+9-3+8} & := \frac{(4+6-7) \times 10}{5-(2-9) \times 3+8} & := \frac{4+6 \times 7-1+0}{5-2+(9-3) \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{(4+6) \times (7-1) + 0}{5 \times 2 \times (9-3) + 8} & := \frac{4+671+0}{5+(2+93) \times 8} & := \frac{4+6+710}{(5+29) \times 3 \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{46759}{81320} & := \frac{4 \times (6+7-5) - 9}{8 \times 1 \times (3+2) + 0} & := \frac{(4+6) \times 7 + 5 \times 9}{(8-1+3) \times 20} & := \frac{46 \times (7+5+9)}{(81+3) \times 20} \\
 & := \frac{46 \times (7 \times 5 - 9)}{8 \times (13 \times 20)} & := \frac{46 \times (7+5-9)}{(8+1+3) \times 20} & := \frac{4-6 \times (7-5-9)}{8 \times (1+3^2) + 0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{47628}{90153} & := \frac{4 \times (7-6-2+8)}{(9-0+1) \times 5+3} & := \frac{4^{7-6+2} - 8}{90+1+5 \times 3} & := \frac{4 \times (76+2-8)}{(9+01) \times 53} \\
 & := \frac{4 \times 7 \times (6+2+8)}{901-53} & := \frac{476+28}{901+53} & := \frac{4 \times 7 \times (6+28)}{901 \times (5-3)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{48609}{75123} & := \frac{4-8+6+09}{7+5 \times (1-2+3)} & := \frac{48-6-09}{(7+5 \times 1 \times 2) \times 3} & := \frac{4 \times (8-6+09)}{75+1-2^3} \\
 & := \frac{4+86+09}{75 \times 1 \times 2+3} & := \frac{4+(8-6) \times 09}{7+5-1+23} & := \frac{4+8+6 \times 09}{7 \times 5 \times (1+2) - 3} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{49210}{83657} & := \frac{4+9-2-1+0}{8-3-6 \times (5-7)} & := \frac{4 \times (9+2-1) + 0}{8-3+6+57} & := \frac{49+21+0}{8 \times (3+6+5) + 7} \\
 & := \frac{4 \times (9+21) + 0}{(8+3+6) \times (5+7)} & := \frac{(4+9+2) \times 10}{8 \times (36-5) + 7} & := \frac{(4+9) \times 2 \times 10}{8-(3-65) \times 7}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{49803}{65127} &:= \frac{4+9+8 \times 0 \times 3}{6+5+1-2+7} &:= \frac{(-4+9+8) \times 03}{6+(5 \times (1 \times (2+7)))} &:= \frac{4 \times (9+8) - 03}{6-(5-(12 \times 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{4-9+80+3}{6 \times (5 \times 1 \times 2+7)} &:= \frac{(4+9) \times 8+0 \times 3}{6-5 \times (1-27)} &:= \frac{(4+9) \times (80-3)}{651 \times 2+7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{49815}{73062} &:= \frac{4+9+8-1-5}{7+3-0+6 \times 2} &:= \frac{4+9-8 \times (1-5)}{7-3+062} &:= \frac{4 \times (9-8) \times 15}{7+3^{06-2}} \\
 &:= \frac{(4+9+8 \times 1) \times 5}{7 \times (30-6-2)} &:= \frac{49+81+5}{7 \times 30-6 \times 2} &:= \frac{(4+9+8) \times 15}{7 \times (30+6^2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{51480}{67392} &:= \frac{51-4+8+0}{6+73-9+2} &:= \frac{5 \times (14+8)+0}{6 \times (7 \times 3-9) \times 2} &:= \frac{5 \times (1+4 \times 8)+0}{6^{7+3-9+2}} \\
 &:= \frac{5 \times (1-4+80)}{6 \times (73+9+2)} &:= \frac{(51+4) \times 8+0}{6 \times (7-3+92)} &:= \frac{5+1480}{6 \times (7-3) \times 9^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{52173}{94860} &:= \frac{(5 \times 2+1) \times (7-3)}{94-8-6+0} &:= \frac{5 \times (2-1+7+3)}{(9-4) \times 8+60} &:= \frac{5+21+73}{94+86+0} \\
 &:= \frac{(52-1-7) \times 3}{(9-4) \times 8 \times 6+0} &:= \frac{(5^2-1) \times 7-3}{(9+4-8) \times 60} &:= \frac{5+2 \times (1+7^3)}{(9+4+8) \times 60} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{53941}{60287} &:= \frac{(5+3+9) \times (4-1)}{(6+02) \times 8-7} &:= \frac{(5+3+9) \times 4 \times 1}{6+(02+8) \times 7} &:= \frac{5 \times (3+9+4+1)}{6+02+87} \\
 &:= \frac{5+3+94 \times 1}{60-2+8 \times 7} &:= \frac{(5+3) \times 9 \times 4+1}{60+2^8+7} &:= \frac{5+3 \times (9-4-1)}{6-02+8+7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{54087}{63921} &:= \frac{5+4 \times 08+7}{63-9-2 \times 1} &:= \frac{5+40+87}{6 \times (3 \times 9-2+1)} &:= \frac{540-8+7}{639-2 \times 1} \\
 &:= \frac{5 \times (40+8+7)}{6 \times 3 \times 9 \times 2+1} &:= \frac{5 \times (4+0 \times 8+7)}{(6+3 \times 9) \times 2-1} &:= \frac{5-(4-08) \times 7}{6+3+9+21} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{54630}{92871} &:= \frac{5-4+6+3+0}{9 \times 2 \times (8-7)-1} &:= \frac{5 \times (4-6)+30}{9 \times 2+8+7+1} &:= \frac{5 \times (46-30)}{9 \times 2 \times 8-7-1} \\
 &:= \frac{(5+4-6) \times 30}{9 \times (2+8+7 \times 1)} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 \times (6+3)+0}{9 \times (28+7-1)} &:= \frac{54+6-30}{9-(2-8) \times 7 \times 1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{64025}{97318} &:= \frac{(6+4) \times 02+5}{9+7 \times 3 \times 1+8} &:= \frac{(6+4+0 \times 2) \times 5}{97-3-18} &:= \frac{(6+4) \times 2 \times 5}{(9+7+3 \times 1) \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times 40+2 \times 5}{97 \times (3+1)-8} &:= \frac{(6+4)^{-02+5}}{(9 \times 7 \times 3+1) \times 8} &:= \frac{(6+4)^{02} \times 5}{(97-3+1) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{65934}{71280} &:= \frac{6+5+9 \times (3+4)}{(7+1+2) \times 8+0} &:= \frac{6 \times (5+93)+4}{(7+1^2) \times 80} &:= \frac{659+3+4}{(7+1 \times 2) \times 80} \\
 &:= \frac{6+5+9 \times 3^4}{(7+1+2) \times 80} &:= \frac{(65+9) \times 3 \times 4}{(7-1) \times 2 \times 80} &:= \frac{(65+9) \times (3+4)}{7 \times 1^2 \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{72369}{85140} &:= \frac{7+2 \times (3+6)+9}{8 \times 5 \times 1^{40}} &:= \frac{7 \times (2+3+6)-9}{8 \times (5+1+4)+0} &:= \frac{7+23 \times 6-9}{8 \times 5 \times 1 \times 4+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{72 + (3+6) \times 9}{8 \times 5 + 140} & := \frac{7 - 2 + 369}{8 \times (51+4) + 0} & := \frac{7 \times (2 - 3 + 69)}{8 \times 5 \times 14 + 0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{73194}{86502} & := \frac{7+3 \times 1 \times (9-4)}{8+6 \times (5-02)} & := \frac{7+3+19+4}{8+6+5^{02}} & := \frac{(7+3-1) \times 9-4}{86+5+0 \times 2} \\
 & := \frac{7+3^{1^9 \times 4}}{8 \times (6+5+02)} & := \frac{7 \times ((3-1) \times 9+4)}{(86+5) \times 02} & := \frac{7 \times (3+19) \times 4}{(8+6) \times (50+2)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{78246}{90153} & := \frac{(7-8+2) \times 46}{(9+01) \times 5+3} & := \frac{7 \times (8+2+4) - 6}{90 + (1+5 \times 3)} & := \frac{7 \times (8^2 - 4) - 6}{9 \times 01 \times 53} \\
 & := \frac{782 - 46}{901 - 53} & := \frac{782 + 46}{901 + 53} & := \frac{(7+82) \times 46}{(90-1) \times 53} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{82017}{94635} & := \frac{8-2+01 \times 7}{9+4-6+3+5} & := \frac{8^2 + 01^7}{(9-(4-6) \times 3) \times 5} & := \frac{8 \times (20-1 \times 7)}{(9-4)^{6-3} - 5} \\
 & := \frac{8 \times 20 - 17}{(9-4+6) \times 3 \times 5} & := \frac{8 \times (20-1+7)}{(9-4) \times 6 \times (3+5)} & := \frac{820 - 1^7}{9 \times (4 \times 6 - 3) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{83421}{90675} & := \frac{8+3 \times (4+2-1)}{90-(6+7) \times 5} & := \frac{8-3+42-1}{9+06+7 \times 5} & := \frac{8-3+4^{2+1}}{9 \times 0 \times 6+75} \\
 & := \frac{8+3^4+2+1}{(9+06) \times 7-5} & := \frac{8 \times (3+4)^2 - 1}{90+67 \times 5} & := \frac{8^3 - 4 + 21}{90 \times 6 + 7 \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{84123}{97065} & := \frac{8+4+1^{23}}{9+7-06+5} & := \frac{(8+4+1^2) \times 3}{9 \times (7-06) \times 5} & := \frac{(8 \times (4-1) + 2) \times 3}{9+70+6+5} \\
 & := \frac{(8+4+1) \times 23}{(9 \times 7 + 06) \times 5} & := \frac{8 + (4 \times 1 \times 2)^3}{9 \times 70 - 6 \times 5} & := \frac{8^{4-1} - 2 - 3}{9 \times (7+06) \times 5}
 \end{aligned}$$

• **Four Digit's Numerator**

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{1098}{254736} & := \frac{1^{09} \times 8}{2 - (5^4 - 7) \times (3 - 6)} & := \frac{1 + 09 - 8}{2 - 5 + 473 - 6} & := \frac{1 + 0 \times 98}{2 + 5 \times (4 \times (7 + 3) + 6)} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times 09 + 8}{2 + (5 + 4) \times 73 \times 6} & := \frac{10 + 9 + 8}{(2 + 5^4) \times (7 + 3) - 6} & := \frac{10 + 9 - 8}{2 \times (547 + 3^6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{2967}{415380} & := \frac{2^{9-6} - 7}{4 \times 1 \times 5 \times 3 + 80} & := \frac{(2-9) \times (6-7)}{4 \times 1 \times (5+3 \times 80)} & := \frac{2-9 \times (6-7)}{4 \times 1 \times (5+380)} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times (9+6-7)}{((4+1) \times 5+3) \times 80} & := \frac{2+9-6+7}{(4 \times (1+5) - 3) \times 80} & := \frac{29+6-7}{(4+15 \times 3) \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{3108}{425796} & := \frac{3 - 1^{08}}{4 \times (2+5+7 \times 9) - 6} & := \frac{3 - 10 + 8}{4 + 2 + 5 \times 7 + 96} & := \frac{3 \times (10 + 8)}{(4+2)^5 - 7 \times 9 \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{3 \times (10 - 8)}{(4 \times (25 + 7) + 9) \times 6} & := \frac{3 + 1^{08}}{4 \times (2^5 + 7 \times (9 + 6))} & := \frac{3 + 10 - 8}{4 \times 25 \times 7 - 9 - 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{3276}{189540} &:= \frac{(3-2)^7+6}{1 \times 89 \times 5 - 40} &:= \frac{3 \times (2+7) - 6}{(18+9) \times (5+40)} &:= \frac{(3-2) \times 7 \times 6}{18 \times (95+40)} \\
 &:= \frac{3-2+7+6}{(1+89) \times (5+4) + 0} &:= \frac{3 \times 2 \times 7 \times 6}{(18+9) \times 540} &:= \frac{3 \times (27-6)}{(1+8) \times 9 \times (5+40)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{3507}{148296} &:= \frac{(3+5) \times 07}{1^4 \times 8 \times 296} &:= \frac{3 \times 5 \times 07}{148 \times 2 \times (9+6)} &:= \frac{35+0 \times 7}{(1-4+8) \times 296} \\
 &:= \frac{35+07}{148 \times (2 \times 9-6)} &:= \frac{35-07}{148 \times 2^{9-6}} &:= \frac{350-7}{(1+48) \times 296} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{3546}{210987} &:= \frac{(3-5+4) \times 6}{210+9 \times 8 \times 7} &:= \frac{(3+5-4) \times 6}{(2+10) \times (9+8) \times 7} &:= \frac{3-(5-4)^6}{(2-1) \times (09+8) \times 7} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times (5 \times 4-6)}{21 \times (09+8) \times 7} &:= \frac{3+(5-4)^6}{2 \times 1 \times (09+8) \times 7} &:= \frac{3+5+4-6}{(2+1) \times (09+8) \times 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{3726}{105984} &:= \frac{(3+7+2)^6}{(105-9)^{8-4}} &:= \frac{3 \times (7+2-6)}{(1 \times 05-9+8)^4} &:= \frac{3^{7+2-6}}{(10+5+9) \times 8 \times 4} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times (7-2) \times 6}{10 \times (5-9+8)^4} &:= \frac{3 \times 72 \times 6}{1^{05} \times 9 \times 8^4} &:= \frac{3+726}{(-1 \times 05+9+8)^4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{3879}{256014} &:= \frac{3 \times 8-7-9}{2 \times (5+60+1) \times 4} &:= \frac{3-(8-7)^9}{2 \times (5+60+1^4)} &:= \frac{3 \times (8+7-9)}{(2+5 \times (60-1)) \times 4} \\
 &:= \frac{3+8 \times 7+9}{2 \times (560+1) \times 4} &:= \frac{3+(8-7)^9}{(2+5+60-1) \times 4} &:= \frac{3+8+7-9}{2-5+601-4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{3897}{206541} &:= \frac{3 \times (8-9)+7}{2 \times (065+41)} &:= \frac{3 \times 8-9-7}{(2+06) \times (54-1)} &:= \frac{3 \times 8+9-7}{(20+6) \times (54-1)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3+8-9) \times 7}{(20-6) \times (54-1)} &:= \frac{3+8+9-7}{2^{06}+5^4 \times 1} &:= \frac{38+9-7}{20 \times (65+41)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4073}{215869} &:= \frac{(4+07) \times 3}{(2+1) \times 586-9} &:= \frac{4 \times 0 \times 7+3}{2 \times (1+5+8) \times 6-9} &:= \frac{4+07-3}{2+1+5 \times 86-9} \\
 &:= \frac{4+0 \times 73}{2+(1+5+8) \times (6+9)} &:= \frac{4+0 \times 7-3}{2+1 \times (5-8+6 \times 9)} &:= \frac{40-7+3}{(2+15 \times (8+6)) \times 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4058}{123769} &:= \frac{4 \times (-05+8)}{1 \times 2 \times 3 \times (7+6 \times 9)} &:= \frac{4+0 \times 58}{1 \times 2+3+(7+6) \times 9} &:= \frac{4+058}{1-(2-37) \times 6 \times 9} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (0 \times 5+8)}{1+23 \times 7 \times 6+9} &:= \frac{(4+05) \times 8}{(1+237+6) \times 9} &:= \frac{4 \times 0 \times 5+8}{1+2 \times 3 \times 7 \times 6-9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4086}{375912} &:= \frac{4+0 \times 8+6}{3+7+5 \times 91 \times 2} &:= \frac{4+08-6}{3 \times (7-5+91 \times 2)} &:= \frac{4+0 \times 86}{375-9+1 \times 2} \\
 &:= \frac{4+086}{(3+7 \times 591) \times 2} &:= \frac{4 \times (0 \times 8+6)}{3^7+5+(9-1) \times 2} &:= \frac{4-08+6}{(3-7+5+91) \times 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4158}{230769} &:= \frac{(4+1 \times 5) \times 8}{2 \times (30+7) \times 6 \times 9} &:= \frac{4 \times (15+8)}{2 \times (30+7) \times 69} &:= \frac{4 \times 1^{58}}{230+7-6-9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{4+1^5 \times 8}{(2+30+7 \times 6) \times 9} & := \frac{4+1+5+8}{230+769} & := \frac{4+1+5-8}{2 \times (3+07) \times 6-9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4509}{138276} & := \frac{(4+5) \times 09}{(1^3+8) \times 276} & := \frac{4+5+0 \times 9}{1 \times 3 \times (8+2 \times 7 \times 6)} & := \frac{4+5+09}{(1 \times 3+82+7) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{4+50-9}{(13-8) \times 276} & := \frac{45+09}{(1-3+8) \times 276} & := \frac{45-09}{138 \times (2 \times 7-6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4536}{109872} & := \frac{(4+5-3) \times 6}{(1+09) \times 87+2} & := \frac{45-36}{109 \times (8-7) \times 2} & := \frac{4+5^3+6}{109 \times (8+7) \times 2} \\
 & := \frac{4 \times 5 \times (3+6)}{109 \times 8 \times (7-2)} & := \frac{(4+5) \times 36}{1 \times 09 \times 872} & := \frac{4 \times 5 \times 3 \times 6}{(1+09) \times 872} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4680}{219375} & := \frac{4 \times 6-8+0}{2 \times 1^9 \times 375} & := \frac{4 \times 6+8+0}{(21+9^3) \times (7-5)} & := \frac{(4+6) \times 8+0}{(2-1+9) \times 375} \\
 & := \frac{4 \times 6 \times 8+0}{(21+9^3) \times (7+5)} & := \frac{4 \times (6+8)+0}{(2 \times 19-3) \times 75} & := \frac{4+68+0}{(2-1) \times 9 \times 375} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4765}{123890} & := \frac{4-(7-6)^5}{1-2-3-8+90} & := \frac{4 \times (7-6)^5}{1+2+3+8+90} & := \frac{4+(7-6) \times 5}{(1 \times 2+3 \times 8) \times 9+0} \\
 & := \frac{(4-7+6) \times 5}{1^2+389+0} & := \frac{4 \times 7 \times (6-5)}{1 \times 2^3+8 \times 90} & := \frac{4+(7-6)^5}{1 \times 2+38+90} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4961}{307582} & := \frac{4 \times 9-6-1}{3 \times 075 \times 8-2} & := \frac{4-9+6 \times 1}{3 \times (07+5+8)+2} & := \frac{4-9+6+1}{30+7+5+82} \\
 & := \frac{4+9-6 \times 1}{(3 \times 075-8) \times 2} & := \frac{49-6-1}{3+(-07+58)^2} & := \frac{49-6+1}{30 \times 7 \times (5+8)-2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4968}{352107} & := \frac{(4-9+6) \times 8}{3^{5-2+1} \times 07} & := \frac{4 \times 9+68}{(3+5 \times 210) \times 7} & := \frac{4^{9-6}+8}{3^{5+2-1} \times 07} \\
 & := \frac{4 \times (9+6) \times 8}{3^5 \times 2 \times 10 \times 7} & := \frac{4 \times (9-6) \times 8}{3^5 \times (21+07)} & := \frac{4 \times 9 \times (6+8)}{3^5 \times 21 \times 07} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4972}{153680} & := \frac{4 \times (9+7)+2}{(1+5-3) \times 680} & := \frac{4-9+7^2}{(1 \times 5-3) \times 680} & := \frac{4 \times (97+2)}{(15+3) \times 680} \\
 & := \frac{4+9+7+2}{1^{53} \times 680} & := \frac{4+97 \times 2}{(1+5+3) \times 680} & := \frac{4+97-2}{15 \times 3 \times 68+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5103}{278964} & := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 03}{2 \times ((78-9) \times 6-4)} & := \frac{5+1+03}{2+7 \times (8 \times 9-6+4)} & := \frac{5+1^{03}}{2 \times 7 \times (8 \times (9-6)-4)} \\
 & := \frac{5+1-03}{(2-7-8+9 \times 6) \times 4} & := \frac{5+10+3}{2 \times 7 \times 8 \times 9-6 \times 4} & := \frac{5+10-3}{(2 \times (7+8 \times 9)+6) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5106}{423798} & := \frac{5-1^{06}}{4 \times (2 \times 3+79)-8} & := \frac{5-1+06}{4 \times 2^3+798} & := \frac{5-10+6}{4+2-3 \times 7+98} \\
 & := \frac{5 \times (10-6)}{4+(2+3 \times 7) \times 9 \times 8} & := \frac{5 \times 1^{06}}{423-7-9+8} & := \frac{5+1+06}{4^2+(3+7) \times 98}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5310}{269748} &:= \frac{5 \times 3 - 10}{2 \times (6 + 97) + 48} &:= \frac{(5 + 3) \times 10}{2^{6 \times (9-7)} - 4 \times 8} &:= \frac{5 \times (3 - 1) + 0}{2 + 6 \times (9 + 74) + 8} \\
 &:= \frac{5 \times 3 \times 1 + 0}{2 - (6 - 97 - 4) \times 8} &:= \frac{5 \times (3 + 1) + 0}{2^{6+9-7} \times 4 - 8} &:= \frac{5 + 3 \times 10}{2 + 6 \times (9 + 7 \times 4) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5328}{190476} &:= \frac{5 \times 32 + 8}{(1 + 90) \times (4 + 7) \times 6} &:= \frac{(5 - 3) \times 28}{(1 + 90) \times (4 \times 7 - 6)} &:= \frac{5 - 3^2 + 8}{1 + 90 + 4 \times (7 + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{5 - 3 + 2 + 8}{1 \times 9 \times 047 + 6} &:= \frac{5 - 3 - 2 + 8}{(1 + 9) \times 04 \times 7 + 6} &:= \frac{5 + 3 + 2 \times 8}{(190 - 47) \times 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5378}{164029} &:= \frac{5 \times 3 - 7 + 8}{16 - 40 + 2^9} &:= \frac{5 \times 3 + 7 - 8}{1 + 6 \times (40 \times 2 - 9)} &:= \frac{5 - 3 \times (7 - 8)}{1 + 6 \times (40 + 2) - 9} \\
 &:= \frac{5 + 3 \times (7 - 8)}{1 + 6 + (4 + 02) \times 9} &:= \frac{53 - 7 + 8}{1640 - 2 + 9} &:= \frac{53 + 7 - 8}{1 - 6 + 40^2 - 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5490}{237168} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 + 90}{(2 + 37 \times 16) \times 8} &:= \frac{(5 + 4) \times 90}{2 \times 3^7 \times 16^6 \times 8} &:= \frac{5 - 4 + 9 + 0}{(2 + 3 + 7 \times (1 + 6)) \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{5 \times 4 \times 9 + 0}{(23 \times 7 + 1) \times 6 \times 8} &:= \frac{54 - 9 + 0}{(237 + 1 \times 6) \times 8} &:= \frac{54 \times 90}{2 \times 3^7 \times 1 \times 6 \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5679}{318024} &:= \frac{5 \times (6 - 7) + 9}{3 \times 1 \times 80 - 2^4} &:= \frac{(5 + 6 - 7) \times 9}{(3 + 1 + 80) \times 24} &:= \frac{(5 - 6) \times (7 - 9)}{3 \times 18 \times 02 + 4} \\
 &:= \frac{5 - 6 \times (7 - 9)}{(3 \times 1 \times 80 - 2) \times 4} &:= \frac{5 - 6 - 7 + 9}{(3 + 1 + 8 + 02) \times 4} &:= \frac{5 + 6 + 7 - 9}{(3 + 1 + 80) \times (2 + 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5814}{293607} &:= \frac{5 - 8 + 1 + 4}{2 + 9 \times (3 \times 6 - 07)} &:= \frac{5 + 8 - 1^4}{2 \times 93 + 60 \times 7} &:= \frac{5 + 8 - 1 - 4}{2 + (9 - 3) \times (60 + 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{5 + 8 + 1^4}{(2 + 93 + 6) \times 07} &:= \frac{58 \times 1^4}{2936 - 07} &:= \frac{58 + 14}{29 + 3607} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5982}{317046} &:= \frac{5 - (9 - 8) \times 2}{3 \times 1 \times (7 + 046)} &:= \frac{5 - 9 + 8^2}{3170 + 4 + 6} &:= \frac{5 - 9 + 8 - 2}{(3 - 1) \times (7 + 046)} \\
 &:= \frac{5 - 9 + 82}{31 + 7 + 046^6} &:= \frac{5 + (9 - 8) \times 2}{3 + (1 + 7) \times 046} &:= \frac{5 + 9 - 8 - 2}{3 \times 1 \times 70 - 4 + 6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6082}{349715} &:= \frac{6 \times 0 \times 8 + 2}{3 + 4 + 9 \times (7 + 1 \times 5)} &:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 8 + 2}{(3 \times 4 + 9 + 71) \times 5} &:= \frac{6 + 08 - 2}{(3 \times (4 + 9) + 7) \times 15} \\
 &:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 82}{3 - 4 - 9 + 71 \times 5} &:= \frac{6 + 0 \times 8 - 2}{(3 + 49 - 7 + 1) \times 5} &:= \frac{60 + 8 - 2}{3 \times (4 \times 9 \times 7 + 1) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6207}{459318} &:= \frac{6^2 \times 07}{(4^5 + 9 + 3) \times 18} &:= \frac{6 - 2 + 0 \times 7}{4 + 5 + 9 \times 31 + 8} &:= \frac{6 + 2 \times 0 \times 7}{4 + 5 \times (9 + 3 - 1) \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{6 + 2 + 0 \times 7}{4 \times (5 \times (9 \times 3 + 1) + 8)} &:= \frac{6 + 2 + 07}{4^5 + 93 + 1 - 8} &:= \frac{6 + 2 - 07}{4 + 5 \times (9 - 3 + 1 \times 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6318}{259740} &:= \frac{6^{3-1} \times 8}{(2 + 5 + 9) \times 740} &:= \frac{6 \times 3 \times (1 + 8)}{2 \times 5 \times 9 \times 74 + 0} &:= \frac{6 \times 3 \times 1^8}{(2 \times 5 - 9) \times 740}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{6+3 \times 1^8}{2 \times 5 \times (9+7 \times 4)+0} := \frac{63 \times 1 \times 8}{2 \times (5+9) \times 740} := \frac{63 \times 18}{(2+5) \times 9 \times 740} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6345}{102789} & := \frac{(6-3)^4 \times 5}{(1+02)^{7-8+9}} := \frac{6^3 \times 45}{(1+02)^7 \times 8 \times 9} := \frac{(6+3+4) \times 5}{(102+7+8) \times 9} \\
 & := \frac{(6+3-4) \times 5}{(1+02) \times (7+8) \times 9} := \frac{6+3-4+5}{(1+02+7+8) \times 9} := \frac{6+34+5}{(1+02+78) \times 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6408}{271539} & := \frac{(6-4) \times 08}{2+715-39} := \frac{6 \times 4+08}{(2^7-15) \times (3+9)} := \frac{6 \times 4+0 \times 8}{(2^7 \times 1-5 \times 3) \times 9} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times (4+08)}{(2^7-15) \times 3 \times 9} := \frac{6 \times 4 \times 08}{2715 \times 3-9} := \frac{6^4+0 \times 8}{2 \times ((7-1)^5+3^9)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6480}{192375} & := \frac{6 \times 4+8+0}{(1+9 \times 2) \times (3+7) \times 5} := \frac{(6+4) \times 8+0}{1^9 \times 2375} := \frac{(6+4) \times 80}{(1+9) \times 2375} \\
 & := \frac{(6-4) \times 8+0}{19 \times (2 \times (3+7)+5)} := \frac{6 \times 48+0}{19 \times 2 \times 3 \times 75} := \frac{64+80}{(1+9 \times 2) \times 3 \times 75} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6579}{342108} & := \frac{(6-5)^{79}}{3+42-1+08} := \frac{6 \times 5-7-9}{3^{4+2}-1^{08}} := \frac{6-(5-7) \times 9}{3 \times (42+10) \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{6-5-7+9}{3 \times 4 \times (21-08)} := \frac{6 \times (5+7+9)}{3^{4 \times 2}-1-08} := \frac{65-7 \times 9}{(-3+4^2 \times 1) \times 08} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6738}{195402} & := \frac{6 \times (7+3 \times 8)}{1-9+5402} := \frac{6+7 \times 3-8}{1 \times 9+540+2} := \frac{6+7-3-8}{(1 \times 9+5 \times 4) \times 02} \\
 & := \frac{67-3-8}{19+5+40^2} := \frac{67+3-8}{1 \times 9 \times 5 \times 40-2} := \frac{67-38}{(1 \times 9+5 \times 4)^{02}} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6912}{307584} & := \frac{6 \times 9 \times 1+2}{(307+5) \times 8-4} := \frac{6 \times (9-1)-2}{(30-7) \times (5+84)} := \frac{6 \times (9-1 \times 2)}{3 \times 07 \times (5+84)} \\
 & := \frac{6 \times 9 \times 1^2}{3+075 \times 8 \times 4} := \frac{6 \times 9^{1+2}}{3^{07} \times (5+84)} := \frac{6+9 \times 1 \times 2}{(307-5 \times 8) \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6948}{305712} & := \frac{(6-9+4) \times 8}{((30-5) \times 7+1) \times 2} := \frac{6 \times 9-48}{3^{05}+7 \times (1+2)} := \frac{6-9+4+8}{3 \times (-05+71) \times 2} \\
 & := \frac{6-9-4+8}{3+05+(7-1)^2} := \frac{6+9-4-8}{3 \times (-05+7^{1 \times 2})} := \frac{6+9+4-8}{(3 \times 05+7 \times 1)^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6972}{453180} & := \frac{(6-9+7)^2}{(4+5+3+1) \times 80} := \frac{6-9+7-2}{4+5^3+1^{80}} := \frac{6+9-7 \times 2}{4+53+1 \times 8+0} \\
 & := \frac{6+9-7+2}{(4+5)^3+1-80} := \frac{6+9+7-2}{4 \times (5+(3+1) \times 80)} := \frac{6+97-2}{4+(5-3+1)^8+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7014}{269538} & := \frac{7+0 \times 14}{2+6+9 \times (5+3 \times 8)} := \frac{7+014}{269+538} := \frac{7 \times 01 \times 4}{2-6+9 \times 5 \times 3 \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{7 \times 014}{2 \times ((6+9) \times 5^3+8)} := \frac{70 \times 1^4}{(2-6+9) \times 538} := \frac{70-14}{(2-(6-95) \times 3) \times 8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7036}{214598} &:= \frac{7 \times 0 \times 3 + 6}{2 + (1 + 4 \times 5) \times 9 - 8} := \frac{(7 - 03) \times 6}{(2 + 1) \times (4 \times 59 + 8)} := \frac{7 + 03 + 6}{2 - 1 \times 4 + 5 \times 98} \\
 &:= \frac{7 + 03 - 6}{2 - (1 + 4 \times (5 - 9)) \times 8} := \frac{7 - 03 + 6}{(2 \times 14 + 5) \times 9 + 8} := \frac{70 - 36}{21 \times (4 + 5 \times 9) + 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7084}{129536} &:= \frac{7 + 0 \times 84}{1 \times 2^{9-5-3+6}} := \frac{7 \times 08 \times 4}{(1 + 2 + 9 - 5 - 3)^6} := \frac{7 \times 08^4}{1 \times 2 \times (9 - 5)^{3+6}} \\
 &:= \frac{7 \times (08 + 4)}{12 \times (9 + 5^3 - 6)} := \frac{7 \times (08 - 4)}{1 \times 2^{9 \times 5 - 36}} := \frac{7 \times 084}{1 \times 2^9 \times (5 \times 3 + 6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7098}{163254} &:= \frac{7 \times 09 + 8}{1632 + 5 - 4} := \frac{7 + 0 \times 9 + 8}{1 + 6^3 + 2^5 \times 4} := \frac{7 + 09 + 8}{1 \times 6 \times (3 \times 2^5 - 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{7 + 09 - 8}{1 \times 6 \times 3 \times 2 \times 5 + 4} := \frac{7 + 0 \times 98}{1 + 6^3 - 2 - 54} := \frac{7 - 09 + 8}{1 + 6 + 3 + 2^5 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7104}{253968} &:= \frac{(7 - 1) \times 04}{2 + (53 + 9 \times 6) \times 8} := \frac{(7 + 1) \times 04}{(2 + 5 \times 3 \times 9 + 6) \times 8} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 04}{(2 \times 5 + 3) \times (9 + 68)} \\
 &:= \frac{7 + 1 + 04}{25 + 396 + 8} := \frac{7 + 1^{04}}{2 \times (5 \times 3^{9-6} + 8)} := \frac{7 + 1 - 04}{2 + 53 + 96 - 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7245}{160839} &:= \frac{(7 - 2) \times 4 - 5}{(1 + 60 - 8 \times 3) \times 9} := \frac{(7 - 2 + 4) \times 5}{160 + 839} := \frac{7 \times (2 + 4) \times 5}{(1 \times 6 + 08^3) \times 9} \\
 &:= \frac{7 + 2 \times 4 + 5}{1 \times 6 \times (083 - 9)} := \frac{7 + 2 - 4 + 5}{1 \times 6 + 08 \times 3 \times 9} := \frac{7 + 2 \times (4 - 5)}{(-1 + 6) \times 08 \times 3 - 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7302}{419865} &:= \frac{7 \times 30 - 2}{(4 + 19) \times 8 \times 65} := \frac{7 - 3 + 0 \times 2}{(4 + 19) \times (8 - 6) \times 5} := \frac{7 - 3 - 02}{(4 + 1 + 9 \times (8 - 6)) \times 5} \\
 &:= \frac{7 - 3 + 02}{4 - 1 + 9 \times (8 + 6 \times 5)} := \frac{7 + 3 + 0 \times 2}{(4 + 1) \times (9 + 8 + 6) \times 5} := \frac{7 + 3 - 02}{4 \times 1 \times (9 + 8 + 6) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7596}{108243} &:= \frac{(7 - 5)^{9-6}}{10 + 8 \times (2^4 - 3)} := \frac{7 \times 5 - 9 - 6}{(10 + 8) \times 2^4 - 3} := \frac{(7 - 5) \times 9 + 6}{(108 + 2 + 4) \times 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + 5) \times (9 - 6)}{1 + 08^{2+4-3}} := \frac{7 \times (5 + 9 - 6)}{(10 + 8^2 \times 4) \times 3} := \frac{(7 - 5) \times 9 - 6}{(1 + 08) \times (2^4 + 3)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7602}{345891} &:= \frac{(7 - 6) \times 02}{3 + 4 \times (5 + 8 + 9 \times 1)} := \frac{7 \times 6 - 02}{(3 + 4 + 5 + 8) \times 91} := \frac{7 \times 6 + 0 \times 2}{3 \times (4 - 5 + 8) \times 91} \\
 &:= \frac{7 \times (60 + 2)}{3^{4+5} + 8 \times (9 - 1)} := \frac{76 + 02}{(3 - 4 + 5 \times 8) \times 91} := \frac{76 - 02}{(34 - 5 + 8) \times 91} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7642}{301859} &:= \frac{(7 + 6) \times 4 + 2}{((30 - 1) \times 8 + 5) \times 9} := \frac{(7 - 6 + 4) \times 2}{301 + 85 + 9} := \frac{7 \times 6 \times 4 - 2}{3^{01 \times 8} + 5 - 9} \\
 &:= \frac{7 \times (6 - 4) - 2}{3 - 01 + 8 \times 59} := \frac{(7 - 6) \times (4 + 2)}{30 + (18 + 5) \times 9} := \frac{(7 - 6) \times (4 - 2)}{3 + 01 \times 85 - 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{8042}{317659} &:= \frac{8 + 04 + 2}{31 - (7 - 65) \times 9} := \frac{8 - 0 + 4 - 2}{3 + 1 \times 7 \times (65 - 9)} := \frac{8 - 0 \times 42}{317 - (6 - 5)^9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{8+0-4-2}{3-1-7+6 \times (5+9)} & := \frac{8+0-4+2}{3 \times (1+76+5)-9} & := \frac{80-4 \times 2}{(317-6+5) \times 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{8379}{215460} & := \frac{8-3+7+9}{(2-1) \times (5+4) \times 60} & := \frac{8-3 \times (7-9)}{(2+1^5 \times 4) \times 60} & := \frac{8-3-7+9}{(2+1^{54}) \times 60} \\
 & := \frac{8-3+79}{(2^{1 \times 5}+4) \times 60} & := \frac{8+(3+7) \times 9}{2 \times (1+5 \times 4) \times 60} & := \frac{8+3 \times (7+9)}{(2-1+5) \times 4 \times 60} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{8395}{127604} & := \frac{(8-3+9) \times 5}{(12+7) \times (60-4)} & := \frac{(8+3-9) \times 5}{1 \times 2 \times 76+0 \times 4} & := \frac{8+3 \times 9+5}{1 \times 2 \times 76 \times 04} \\
 & := \frac{8+3 \times 9-5}{12 \times (7 \times 6-04)} & := \frac{8+3 \times (9-5)}{(12-7) \times 60+4} & := \frac{8+3+9-5}{(1+2) \times 76+0 \times 4} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{8532}{174906} & := \frac{8-5+3^2}{1 \times 7 \times 4 \times 9-06} & := \frac{8-5+3+2}{17 \times 4+90+6} & := \frac{8-5-3+2}{(1+7) \times 4+9+0 \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{8 \times (5+3-2)}{(1 \times 74+90) \times 6} & := \frac{8+(5+3) \times 2}{1+7+490-6} & := \frac{8+5-3^2}{1-7+4+90-6} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{8604}{359217} & := \frac{8 \times 6+04}{3^5 \times 9-2 \times (1+7)} & := \frac{(8+6) \times 04}{(3^5+92-1) \times 7} & := \frac{8+6 \times 0 \times 4}{35 \times 9+2+17} \\
 & := \frac{8 \times (6-04)}{3+5 \times (9 \times 2+1) \times 7} & := \frac{8 \times (60-4)}{(3^5 \times (9+2)-1) \times 7} & := \frac{8^{6-04}}{3^5 \times (9+2)-1^7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{8964}{105327} & := \frac{(8+9-6) \times 4}{10 \times (53-2)+7} & := \frac{8+96+4}{(10 \times 5-3) \times 27} & := \frac{8 \times (9-6)+4}{(10+5+32) \times 7} \\
 & := \frac{8 \times 9-64}{10 \times (5+3)+2 \times 7} & := \frac{8 \times (9-6+4)}{10 \times 53+2^7} & := \frac{8 \times (9+6-4)}{10+(5+3) \times 2^7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9153}{467820} & := \frac{9 \times 1 \times (5+3)}{46 \times (78+2)+0} & := \frac{9 \times (1+5 \times 3)}{(4+6 \times 7) \times 8 \times 20} & := \frac{9 \times (1+5-3)}{46 \times (7+8) \times 2+0} \\
 & := \frac{9 \times (15-3)}{(4 \times 67+8) \times 20} & := \frac{9 \times 1^{53}}{4+6 \times (78-2)+0} & := \frac{9+(1+53)}{46 \times 7 \times (8+2)+0} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9234}{108756} & := \frac{9 \times (2-3+4)}{(10+8+7 \times 5) \times 6} & := \frac{9 \times (2+3+4)}{10 \times 8 \times (7+5)-6} & := \frac{9^{2+3-4}}{10+8 \times (7-5) \times 6} \\
 & := \frac{9+2+3+4}{10-8+7 \times 5 \times 6} & := \frac{9+2+34}{10 \times 8 \times 7-5 \times 6} & := \frac{9+23+4}{10 \times (8+7 \times 5)-6}
 \end{aligned}$$

Remark 3.1. From now onwards the expressions are without simplifications, i.e., there are lot of extra bracket, such as, "(...)". These can be removed easily making simplifications.

3.6 7 Equivalent Blocks

- Five Digit's Numerator

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10368}{47952} &:= \frac{((1 - (0 - 3)) \times 6) - 8}{4 + (7 + (9 \times (5 + 2)))} := \frac{1 \times (0 - ((3 - 6) \times 8))}{((4 \times 7) + 9) \times (5 - 2)} := \frac{(1^{03}) \times (6 \times 8)}{4 - (7 - (9 \times (5^2)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - 3)) \times (6 + 8)}{(4 \times (7 \times 9)) + (5 + 2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (3 + 68))}{4 + (7 \times ((9 \times 5) + 2))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (3 + 6))) \times 8}{((4 \times 7) + 9) \times (5 \times 2)} := \frac{(1 - (0 - 3)) \times 68}{(4 \times (7 \times (9 \times 5))) - 2} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{10395}{42768} &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (39 - 5))}{4 \times (2 + ((7 \times 6) - 8))} := \frac{10 \times (3 + (9 - 5))}{4 + (276 + 8)} := \frac{((10 \times 3) - 9) \times 5}{(4 - (2 - 7)) \times (6 \times 8)} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (3 \times 9))) \times 5}{4 \times ((2 \times 76) - 8)} \\ &:= \frac{(10 + 39) \times 5}{(4 + ((2^7) - 6)) \times 8} := \frac{(103 + 9) \times 5}{((42 \times 7) - 6) \times 8} := \frac{10 \times (3 \times (9 + 5))}{4 \times ((2 + 7) \times (6 \times 8))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{10536}{48729} &:= \frac{1 \times ((05 - (3 - 6)))}{4 + (8 + (7 + (2 \times 9)))} := \frac{1 + (0 - (5 - 36))}{4 + (8 \times (7 + (2 + 9)))} := \frac{(10 + (5 - 3)) \times 6}{((4 \times 8) + (7 - 2)) \times 9} := \frac{10 \times (5 - (3 - 6))}{((4 + (8 + 7))^2) + 9} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (5 + (3 \times 6)))}{(4 \times ((8 + 7) \times 2)) - 9} := \frac{(1 - (0 - 5)) \times 36}{487 + (2^9)} := \frac{1 \times (((05 - 3)^6))}{4 \times ((8 \times 7) + (2 \times 9))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{12096}{73584} &:= \frac{1 * ((2 * (09)) - 6)}{(7 * (3 * 5)) - (8 * 4)} := \frac{1^2 \times 096}{((7 + 3) \times 58) + 4} := \frac{1 \times (2 \times ((09 \times 6)))}{73 \times (5 + (8 - 4))} := \frac{12 \times ((09 \times 6))}{73 \times (58 - 4)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (209 - 6)}{73 \times (5 + (8 + 4))} := \frac{1 \times (20 \times 96)}{73 \times (5 \times (8 \times 4))} := \frac{(1 + 20) \times 96}{7 \times (3 \times 584)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{12978}{46350} &:= \frac{1 - (2 - (9 + (7 - 8)))}{4 + (6 + (3 \times (5 - 0)))} := \frac{1 \times (29 - (7 + 8))}{(4 - (6 - 3)) \times 50} := \frac{1 - (((2 - 9) \times 7) + 8)}{(4 + 6) \times (3 \times (5 - 0))} := \frac{(12 - 9) \times (7 \times 8)}{4 \times ((6 - 3) \times 50)} \\ &:= \frac{(1^2) \times (9 \times (7 \times 8))}{4 \times ((6 + 3) \times 50)} := \frac{1 \times (2 + 978)}{(4 + 6) \times 350} := \frac{1 \times (2 \times (9 \times (7 \times 8)))}{4 \times (6 \times (3 \times 50))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{12980}{74635} &:= \frac{1 + (2 + (9 - (8 - 0)))}{7 + (4 \times (6 + (3 - 5)))} := \frac{12 \times (9 - 8) + 0}{7 + (4 + (63 - 5))} := \frac{1 + (2 + (9 + (8 - 0)))}{74 + (6 + 35)} := \frac{((1^2)^9) \times (8 - 0)}{((7 + (4 + 6)) \times 3) - 5} \\ &:= \frac{12 + (9 \times (8 - 0))}{7 \times ((46^{-3}) + 5)} := \frac{1 \times (2 \times 980)}{7 \times (46 \times 35)} := \frac{((1^2)^9) \times 80}{(74 + (6 \times 3)) \times 5} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{13480}{92675} &:= \frac{1 + (3 - (4 - (8 - 0)))}{(9 - (2 \times (6 - 7))) \times 5} := \frac{1 + (3 + (4 + (8 - 0)))}{9 + (26 + 75)} := \frac{(1^3) \times (48 - 0)}{(9 + ((2^6) - 7)) \times 5} := \frac{1 + (3 - (4 - 80))}{(92 \times 6) - (7 - 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (3 \times 4)) \times (8 - 0)}{(9 + (2 \times 67)) \times 5} := \frac{(13 - 4) \times 80}{(9 + 2) \times (6 \times 75)} := \frac{(1 + 3) \times (4 + 80)}{(9 + 2) \times (6 \times (7 \times 5))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{13869}{54270} &:= \frac{1 \times (38 - (6 + 9))}{5 \times (4 + (2 \times (7 - 0)))} := \frac{1 + ((3 + (8 - 6)) \times 9)}{5 \times (4 \times (2 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{1 \times (38 + (6 \times 9))}{5 \times (4 - (2 - 70))} := \frac{1 - (3 \times (8 - 69))}{5 \times (4 + (2 \times 70))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times (8 + (6 + 9)))}{(5 - 4) \times 270} := \frac{((1^3) + 8) \times 69}{(5 + 4) \times 270} := \frac{(13 + 8) \times 69}{((5 + 4)^2) \times 70} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{13950}{26784} &:= \frac{((1 + 3)^9) \times 50}{((2 + 6)^7) \times (8 + 4)} := \frac{((1^3)^9) \times 50}{2 + ((6 \times (7 + 8)) + 4)} := \frac{(1 - (3 - 9)) \times 50}{2 \times ((6 + 78) \times 4)} := \frac{(1 + (3 \times 9)) \times 50}{2 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (39 \times 50)}{2 \times (6 \times (78 \times 4))} := \frac{(1^3) \times 950}{((2^6) - 7) \times (8 \times 4)} := \frac{(1 + 39) \times 50}{(2^6) \times ((7 + 8) \times 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{14098}{76532} &:= \frac{1 - (4 + (0 - (9 + 8)))}{(7 \times (6 + 5)) - (3 - 2)} := \frac{1 \times (4 - (0 - (9 + 8)))}{((7 \times 6) + (5 \times 3)) \times 2} := \frac{((1 - 4) \times (0 - 9)) + 8}{((7 \times 6) + 53) \times 2} := \frac{1^4 \times 098}{(7 - 6) \times 532} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (4 - (0 - 9))) \times 8}{76 + 532} := \frac{140 \times (9 - 8)}{76 \times (5 + (3 + 2))} := \frac{14 \times ((09 + 8))}{76 \times ((5 \times 3) + 2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14265}{37089} &:= \frac{1 + (4^{2-6+5})}{3 - (7 + (0 - (8 + 9)))} := \frac{(1 + (4 - (2 - 6))) \times 5}{((3 \times (7 - 0)) - 8) \times 9} := \frac{(1 + ((4 \times 2) + 6)) \times 5}{3 \times ((7 \times (08)) + 9)} := \frac{(1 - (4 - 26)) \times 5}{(3 \times 70) + 89} \\ &:= \frac{((14 \times 2) + 6) \times 5}{370 + (8 \times 9)} := \frac{(1 + (4 - 2)) \times 65}{3 - (7 \times (0 - (8 \times 9)))} := \frac{1 + (4 + 265)}{3 + (708 - 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14360}{98725} &:= \frac{1 + (4 - (3 - (6 - 0)))}{9 - (8 - ((7^2) + 5))} := \frac{((1^4) + 3) \times (6 - 0)}{98 + (72 - 5)} := \frac{1 \times (4 + (36 - 0))}{(9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 2)) + 5} := \frac{(1 + (4 + 3)) \times (6 - 0)}{(9 + (8 + (7^2))) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (4 \times (3 \times (6 - 0)))}{9 \times (87 - (2^5))} := \frac{1 + (43 + 60)}{(9 \times (8 + 72)) - 5} := \frac{1 \times (4 \times (36 - 0))}{9 \times ((8 + (7 \times 2)) \times 5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14679}{50328} &:= \frac{1 \times (4 - (6 - (7 + 9)))}{(5 - (0 - (3 - 2))) \times 8} := \frac{1 - ((4 + 6) \times (7 - 9))}{((5 - (0 - 3))^2) + 8} := \frac{1 - (4 + (6 - 79))}{5 \times ((03 \times (2 \times 8)))} := \frac{1 \times (4 - (6 - 79))}{5 - (0 - (3 + (2^8)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (4 + (6 - (7 + 9)))}{5 - (0 - (3 + (2 \times 8)))} := \frac{1 - (4 \times (6 \times (7 - 9)))}{(5 \times (032)) + 8} := \frac{1 + (4 \times ((6 + 7) \times 9))}{(50 \times 32) + 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14760}{23985} &:= \frac{(1 - (4 - 7)) \times (6 - 0)}{(2^3) - (9 - (8 \times 5))} := \frac{14 + (7 \times (6 - 0))}{(2 \times 39) + (8 + 5)} := \frac{1 - (4 - (7 + 60))}{2 \times (3 + (9 + (8 \times 5)))} := \frac{1 + (4 + (7 + 60))}{((2 + (3 + 9)) \times 8) + 5} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (4 + (76 - 0))}{((2 + 3) \times 9) + 85} := \frac{(1 - (4 - 7)) \times 60}{((2 \times 3) + (9 \times 8)) \times 5} := \frac{(1^4) \times 760}{(239 + 8) \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{15498}{73062} &:= \frac{((1 + 5) \times 4) - (9 + 8)}{7 + (30 - (6 - 2))} := \frac{(1^5) - (4 - (9 + 8))}{7 - (3 + (0 - 62))} := \frac{1 + (5 \times (4 \times (9 - 8)))}{7 + (30 + 62)} := \frac{(1^5) + (49 - 8)}{(7 \times 30) - (6 \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (5 - (4 + 98))}{7 \times (30 + (6^2))} := \frac{1 + ((5 + 4) \times (9 + 8))}{730 - (6 - 2)} := \frac{(1 + 5) \times ((4 \times 9) - 8)}{730 + 62} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{15780}{36294} &:= \frac{1 \times (5 + (7 + (8 - 0)))}{36 + (2 \times (9 - 4))} := \frac{15 + (7 + (8 - 0))}{3 - (6 \times (2 - (9 + 4)))} := \frac{1 + (57 - (8 - 0))}{3 + ((6 \times (2 \times 9)) + 4)} := \frac{((1^5)^7) \times 80}{(((3 \times 6) + 2) \times 9) + 4} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 5) \times (7 + (8 - 0))}{3 - (6 \times (2 - (9 \times 4)))} := \frac{(1 - (5 - 7)) \times 80}{36 + ((2^9) + 4)} := \frac{1 \times (5 \times (7 \times (8 - 0)))}{(36 \times (2 \times 9)) - 4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{16032}{48597} &:= \frac{1^6 \times 032}{(4 - (8 - 5)) \times 97} := \frac{16^{0 \times 3 + 2}}{4 + ((85 \times 9) + 7)} := \frac{160 \times 32}{4 \times (8 \times (5 \times 97))} := \frac{(1 + (60 + 3)) \times 2}{485 - 97} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (6 \times (032))}{485 + 97} := \frac{(1 + (6 - 0)) \times 32}{(4 + (8 - 5)) \times 97} := \frac{1 \times (60 \times 32)}{(4 + 8) \times (5 \times 97)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{16952}{78403} &:= \frac{(1^6) \times (9 + (5 + 2))}{78 - (4 - (0 \times 3))} := \frac{1 \times (6 \times ((9 - 5) \times 2))}{(78 - (4 - 0)) \times 3} := \frac{1 - (6 - (9 + 52))}{7 - (84 \times (0 - 3))} := \frac{1 \times (6 \times (9 + (5 - 2)))}{(7 \times (8 + 40)) - 3} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (6 + (95 + 2))}{78 + 403} := \frac{(1 + ((6 \times 9) + 5)) \times 2}{(7 + 8) \times (40 - 3)} := \frac{16 \times ((9 + 5) \times 2)}{7 \times (8 \times (40 - 3))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{17068}{23594} &:= \frac{1 \times ((7 \times (06)) - 8)}{(2 \times 3) + (5 + (9 \times 4))} := \frac{1 \times (70 + (6 - 8))}{2 + (3 - (5 - 94))} := \frac{170 - 68}{2 + ((3 \times (5 \times 9)) + 4)} := \frac{17 \times (068)}{(2 + (3 \times 5)) \times 94} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (70 \times 68)}{2 \times (35 \times 94)} := \frac{17 \times ((06 + 8))}{((2 + 35) \times 9) - 4} := \frac{17 \times ((0 \times 6) + 8)}{(27^3) + (5 \times (9 \times 4))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{17892}{34506} &:= \frac{(1 + (7 + (8 - 9))) \times 2}{3^{4+5-06}} := \frac{1 - (7 - ((8 + 9) \times 2))}{(3 \times (4 \times (5 - 0))) - 6} := \frac{1 + (7 + ((8 + 9) \times 2))}{3^{4-5 \times 0 \times 6}} := \frac{(1^7) \times ((8 \times 9) - 2)}{3 \times (45 - (0 \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (7 \times (8 + (9 \times 2)))}{345 - (0 - 6)} := \frac{1 \times (7 \times ((8 + 9) \times 2))}{3 + (450 + 6)} := \frac{(1 - 7) \times (8 - 92)}{3 \times ((4 + 50) \times 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{18423}{76095} &:= \frac{1 \times (84 + (2^3))}{(7 + (60 + 9)) \times 5} := \frac{(1^{84}) \times 23}{(7 - (6 - 0)) \times 95} := \frac{1 + (8 \times (4 \times (2 + 3)))}{760 - 95} := \frac{184 + 23}{760 + 95} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (8 + 4)) \times 23}{(7 + (6 - 0)) \times 95} := \frac{1 \times (8 \times (4 \times 23))}{760 \times (9 - 5)} := \frac{(1 + 8) \times (4 \times 23)}{76 \times ((09 \times 5))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{18675}{23904} &:= \frac{1 + ((8 - 6) \times (7 + 5))}{2 \times (3 + (9 - (0 - 4)))} := \frac{1 + ((8 \times (6 + 7)) - 5)}{(23 + (9 - 0)) \times 4} := \frac{(1 + (8 - 6)) \times 75}{(2^3) \times (9 \times (04))} := \frac{(1 - (8 - 67)) \times 5}{((2 \times 3) + 90) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (86 - (7 + 5))}{2 \times ((3 + (9 - 0)) \times 4)} := \frac{(18 + 67) \times 5}{(2 \times (3 \times 90)) + 4} := \frac{(1 + 8) \times 675}{(2 \times 3)^{9-04}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{19548}{60273} &:= \frac{(1 + (9 - 5)) \times (4 + 8)}{60 + ((2^7) - 3)} := \frac{1 + (9 + (54 + 8))}{(60 + (2 \times 7)) \times 3} := \frac{1 + (95 - (4 + 8))}{602 - (7^3)} := \frac{1 \times (9 \times ((5 \times 4) - 8))}{60 + 273} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((9 + (5 + 4)) \times 8)}{60 + ((2^7) \times 3)} := \frac{1 \times ((9 - 5) \times 48)}{602 - (7 + 3)} := \frac{1 - (9 + (5 \times (4 - 8)))}{60 - (2 + (7 \times 3))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{19872}{43056} &:= \frac{1 \times (9 - (8 - (7 - 2)))}{4 - ((3 \times (0 - 5)) + 6)} := \frac{1 \times (9 + (8 - (7 - 2)))}{(4 \times (3 - (0 - 5))) - 6} := \frac{1 + ((9 \times 8) - (7^2))}{4 + ((3 - (0 - 5)) \times 6)} := \frac{(1^9) \times ((8 + 7) \times 2)}{4^3 - 05 + 6} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (98 + (7 + 2))}{(4 + (30 + 5)) \times 6} := \frac{1 \times (9 \times (8 + (7 \times 2)))}{430 + (5 - 6)} := \frac{1 \times ((98 \times 7) - 2)}{(4 + (3^{05})) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{19872}{56304} &:= \frac{1 \times (9 - (8 - (7 - 2)))}{5 + ((6 - (3 - 0)) \times 4)} := \frac{1 + ((9 \times 8) - (7^2))}{5 + (63 - (0 \times 4))} := \frac{(1^9) - (8 - (7^2))}{5 - (6 - (30 \times 4))} := \frac{(1 - (9 - (8 \times 7))) \times 2}{(5 + (63 - 0)) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (9 + (8 \times 7))) \times 2}{(5 + 6) \times (30 + 4)} := \frac{1 \times (9 \times (8 \times (7 - 2)))}{5 \times (6 \times (30 + 4))} := \frac{1 + ((9 \times 8) + (7 - 2))}{5 + (6^{3-0 \times 4})} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{21456}{93870} &:= \frac{2 \times ((1 - (4 - 5)) \times 6)}{(9 \times 3) + (8 + 70)} := \frac{2^{1 \times (4-5+6)}}{(9 + (3 + 8)) \times (7 - 0)} := \frac{2 + (1 \times ((4 + 5) \times 6))}{((9 \times 3) + 8) \times (7 - 0)} := \frac{(2 - 1) \times (4 \times 56)}{(9 - (3 - 8)) \times 70} \\ &:= \frac{2^{1+4-5+6}}{(9 + (3 - 8)) \times 70} := \frac{2 \times ((1 + 4) \times 56)}{((9 \times 3) + 8) \times 70} := \frac{2 \times (((1^4) + 5)^6)}{(9^3) \times (8 \times 70)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{21730}{56498} &:= \frac{2 \times (1 + (7 - (3 - 0)))}{(5^{6-4}) + (9 - 8)} := \frac{2 - (17 - 30)}{5 - (6 + ((4 - 9) \times 8))} := \frac{2 \times (1 \times (7 + (3 - 0)))}{5 + (6 + (49 - 8))} := \frac{2 - (1 - (7 - (3 - 0)))}{5 + ((6 + (4 - 9)) \times 8)} \\ &:= \frac{(2^{1 \times 7}) - (3 - 0)}{5 \times (64 + (9 - 8))} := \frac{(2 - (1 - 7)) \times 30}{(5 + (64 + 9)) \times 8} := \frac{(2 + 1 + 7)^3 + 0}{5 \times (((6 - 4)^9) + 8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{23495}{61087} &:= \frac{2 + (3 - (4 - (9 - 5)))}{6 + ((1^{08}) \times 7)} := \frac{(2 - (3 + (4 - 9))) \times 5}{6 - (10 - (8 \times 7))} := \frac{((2 \times (3 - 4)) + 9) \times 5}{(6 - (1 + (0 - 8))) \times 7} := \frac{(2 \times (34 - 9)) - 5}{61 - (0 - (8 \times 7))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (3 - (4 + 9))) \times 5}{6 + (10 \times (8 + 7))} := \frac{(23 - (4 - 9)) \times 5}{((6 \times 10) - 8) \times 7} := \frac{2 + (3 + (4 \times (9 \times 5)))}{(61 \times (08)) - 7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23571}{89046} &:= \frac{(2 \times (3 - (5 - 7))) - 1}{(8 \times (9 + (0 - 4))) - 6} := \frac{((2 - (3 - 5)) \times 7) - 1}{(8 + (9 - (0 \times 4))) \times 6} := \frac{2 + (3 + (5 \times (7 + 1)))}{(8 + (9 - 0)) \times (4 + 6)} := \frac{23 + (5 + 71)}{8 + ((90 \times 4) + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + ((3 \times (5 \times 7)) + 1)}{(8 + (9 - 0)) \times (4 \times 6)} := \frac{235 + (7 + 1)}{8 + (904 + 6)} := \frac{(2^3) \times ((5 \times 7) + 1)}{8 \times (90 + 46)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25137}{40698} &:= \frac{2 + (5 - ((1 - 3) \times 7))}{40 - (6 \times (9 - 8))} := \frac{2 + (5 \times ((1^3) + 7))}{(4 \times ((06 + 9))) + 8} := \frac{(2 + (5 - (1 - 3))) \times 7}{4 - ((0 \times 6) - 98)} := \frac{((2 \times (5 + 1)) + 3) \times 7}{(4 - (0 - 6)) \times (9 + 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times ((5 + 13) \times 7)}{4 \times ((06 \times (9 + 8)))} := \frac{2513 + 7}{40 \times (6 \times (9 + 8))} := \frac{((2 + (5 - 1))^3) \times 7}{(40 - 6) \times (9 \times 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25890}{67314} &:= \frac{(2^5) - (8 + (9 - 0))}{(6 + 7) \times (3 \times (1^4))} := \frac{(2 \times (5 + 8)) + (9 - 0)}{(6 + 7) \times (3 + (1 \times 4))} := \frac{((2 + 5) \times 8) + (9 - 0)}{(6 + 7)^{3-1^4}} := \frac{(2 + (5 + 8)) \times (9 - 0)}{(6 + 7) \times (31 - 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (5 \times (8 + (9 - 0)))}{(6 \times (73 \times 1)) + 4} := \frac{((2 \times 5) - 8) \times 90}{6 \times (73 + (1 + 4))} := \frac{2 \times ((5 \times 8) + 90)}{673 - (1 - 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{26150}{39748} &:= \frac{26 - 1^5 + 0}{3 + 9 \times (7 - 4) + 8} := \frac{2 \times ((6 - 1) \times (5 - 0))}{3 - (9 - (74 + 8))} := \frac{26 - (1 - 50)}{3 + ((9 \times 7) + 48)} := \frac{2 \times (6 \times (1 \times 50))}{(3 + (9 + 7)) \times 48} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (6 \times 1)) \times 50}{(3 + (9 + 7)) \times (4 \times 8)} := \frac{(2^{6-1}) \times 50}{39 + ((7^4) - 8)} := \frac{2 \times ((6 - 1) \times 50)}{3 + (9 + 748)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{26890}{45713} &:= \frac{2 \times (6 + (8 - (9 - 0)))}{4 + (5 + (7 + (1^3)))} := \frac{2 - ((6 - 8) \times (9 - 0))}{4 - (5 \times (7 - 13))} := \frac{2 + (6 + (8 \times (9 - 0)))}{4 \times ((5 \times 7) - (1^3))} := \frac{2 + (6 - (8 - 90))}{(4 \times (5 \times 7)) + 13} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times 6) + 8) \times 90}{45 \times (71 - 3)} := \frac{(2 - (6 - 8)) \times 90}{(4 + 5) \times (71 - 3)} := \frac{2 + (6 \times (8 + 90))}{(4^5) - (7 \times (1 \times 3))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29106}{45738} &:= \frac{2 + (9 - (10 - 6))}{4 - (5 - (7 - (3 - 8)))} := \frac{(2 \times (9 + (1 - 0))) - 6}{4 + (5 + ((7 \times 3) - 8))} := \frac{2 \times (9 - (1 + (0 - 6)))}{4 - (5 - (7 + 38))} := \frac{29 - (1 \times (0 - 6))}{(4 \times 5) - (7 \times (3 - 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (9 \times 1)) \times (0 - 6)}{4 + (57 - (3 - 8))} := \frac{2 \times (91 - (0 \times 6))}{(4^5) - 738} := \frac{2 - (9 \times (1 \times (0 - 6)))}{4 \times (5 - (7 - (3 \times 8)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29160}{47385} &:= \frac{2 \times (9 + (1 - (6 - 0)))}{4 - (7 - (3 + (8 + 5)))} := \frac{2 \times (9 - (1^6 + 0))}{4 - (7 - ((3 \times 8) + 5))} := \frac{2 + (9 + (1 + 60))}{4 - (7 - (3 \times (8 \times 5)))} := \frac{2 \times ((9 + 1) \times (6 - 0))}{(4 - (7 \times (3 - 8))) \times 5} \\
 &:= \frac{(2^9) + 160}{4 \times (7 \times (3 \times (8 + 5)))} := \frac{2 \times (9 + (1 + (6 - 0)))}{4 \times (7 + (3 + (8 - 5)))} := \frac{(2^9) - 160}{(47 - 3) \times (8 + 5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29376}{51408} &:= \frac{(2 \times (9 + (3 - 7))) + 6}{(5 \times (1 \times (4 - 0))) + 8} := \frac{2 + (9 - (3 \times (7 - 6)))}{5 + ((1^4 + 0) + 8)} := \frac{2 \times (9 + (3 \times (7 + 6)))}{((5 - 1) \times 40) + 8} := \frac{(2^{9-3}) + 76}{5 \times (1 + (40 + 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(29 + 3) \times (7 + 6)}{(51 + 40) \times 8} := \frac{2 \times (9 \times (3 - (7 - 6)))}{51 + (4 - (0 - 8))} := \frac{2 \times (93 + (7 + 6))}{51 + (40 \times 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30129}{68475} &:= \frac{3 - (0 - (1 - (2 - 9)))}{(6 \times (8 + (4 - 7))) - 5} := \frac{3 - (0 - (1 + (2 \times 9)))}{6 - (8 - (47 + 5))} := \frac{3 - (0 - (1 + 29))}{((6 + (8 - 4)) \times 7) + 5} := \frac{(3 - (0 - 1)) \times (2 + 9)}{(6 + (8 - 4))^{7-5}} \\
 &:= \frac{(30 \times (1 + 2)) + 9}{(6 - (8 - 47)) \times 5} := \frac{3 - (0 - 129)}{6 \times (8 + (47 - 5))} := \frac{30 \times (1 \times (2 + 9))}{(6 + (8 - 4)) \times 75} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30294}{87516} &:= \frac{3 \times (0 - (2 - (9 - 4)))}{8 + (7 - (5 - 16))} := \frac{3 - (0 - (2 + (9 + 4)))}{87 - (5 \times (1 + 6))} := \frac{3^{-02+9-4}}{8 + (7 \times (5 - (1 - 6)))} := \frac{3 - (0 - (29 + 4))}{8 \times (7 + (5 + (1^6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{3 - (0 - (2 + 94))}{(8 \times (7 \times (5 \times 1))) + 6} := \frac{3 \times ((0 \times 2) + (9 \times 4))}{(8 - (7 - 51)) \times 6} := \frac{3 \times ((02 \times (9 \times 4)))}{8 \times ((7 + (5 + 1)) \times 6)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{31052}{48796} &:= \frac{3 + (1 - (0 - (5 - 2)))}{4 + (((8 - 7)^9) + 6)} := \frac{3 + (1 - (0 - (5 \times 2)))}{4 + (8 + (7 + (9 - 6)))} := \frac{3 \times (1 \times ((05 + 2)))}{4 + (8 + (7 \times (9 - 6)))} := \frac{3 + (1 - (0 - 52))}{4 + (87 - (9 - 6))} \\ &:= \frac{((3 + 10) \times 5) - 2}{4 - (8 - (7 + 96))} := \frac{3 \times (10 + (5^2))}{((4 + (8 + 7)) \times 9) - 6} := \frac{3 - (1 \times (0 - (5^2)))}{4 - ((8 \times 7) - 96)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{31695}{82407} &:= \frac{3 + (1 \times (6 - (9 - 5)))}{8 + (2 - (4 + (0 - 7)))} := \frac{3 \times (1 \times (6 + (9 - 5)))}{82 - (4 - (0 \times 7))} := \frac{(3 \times (1 \times (6 + 9))) - 5}{8 \times (2 + (4 - (0 - 7)))} := \frac{(3 - (1 - (6 \times 9))) \times 5}{((8^2) + 40) \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{3 + (16 - (9 - 5))}{8 - (2 - (40 - 7))} := \frac{(3 + (1 + (6 + 9))) \times 5}{((8 - 2) \times 40) + 7} := \frac{(3 - (1 - 6)) \times 95}{8 \times (240 + 7)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{31728}{69405} &:= \frac{3 + (1 \times (7 - (2 - 8)))}{6 + (9 - (4 \times (0 - 5)))} := \frac{(3 + (1^{72})) \times 8}{69 - (4 + (0 - 5))} := \frac{3 + (17 + 28)}{6 + (94 - (0 - 5))} := \frac{(3 + (1 \times (7 + 2))) \times 8}{(6 + (9 \times (4 - 0))) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (1 \times (72 - 8))}{6 + (9 + 405)} := \frac{3 \times (1 \times (72 + 8))}{(6 + 9) \times (40 - 5)} := \frac{3 \times ((1 + 7) \times 28)}{6 \times ((9 + 40) \times 5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{31790}{82654} &:= \frac{3 - (1 \times (7 - (9 - 0)))}{8 - (2 - (6 + (5 - 4)))} := \frac{3 + (1 + (7 + (9 - 0)))}{8 + ((2^6) - (5 \times 4))} := \frac{3 \times ((1^7) + (9 - 0))}{82 - ((6 - 5) \times 4)} := \frac{(3 \times 17) + (9 - 0)}{(8 + (26 + 5)) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{3 + (1 \times (7 + 90))}{8 - ((2 - 65) \times 4)} := \frac{3 + (17 + 90)}{((8^2) - 6) \times 5 - 4} := \frac{(3 + 17) \times (9 - 0)}{(8 \times ((2^6) - 5)) - 4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{32064}{79158} &:= \frac{320 - 64}{79 \times ((1^5) \times 8)} := \frac{(3 \times (2 \times (06))) - 4}{7 + (9 \times ((1^5) \times 8))} := \frac{32^{06-4}}{(7 + 9) \times 158} := \frac{3 \times (20 \times 64)}{79 \times (15 \times 8)} \\ &:= \frac{32 \times (064)}{((7 \times 91) - 5) \times 8} := \frac{32 \times ((0 \times 6) + 4)}{79 \times (1 - (5 - 8))} := \frac{3 \times ((2 - (0 - 6)) \times 4)}{79 + 158} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{32096}{58174} &:= \frac{3 - (2 + (0 - (9 + 6)))}{5 + (8 \times (1 \times (7 - 4)))} := \frac{(3 \times (2 \times (09))) - 6}{5 + (8 + (1 \times 74))} := \frac{(3 - (2 - 0)) \times 96}{58 \times (1 \times (7 - 4))} := \frac{32 - (0 - 96)}{58 \times (1 + (7 - 4))} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (2^{0 \times 9 + 6})}{5 + ((8 - 1)^{7-4})} := \frac{32 - (0 \times 96)}{5 + (81 - (7 \times 4))} := \frac{320 + 96}{58 \times (17 - 4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{32901}{47856} &:= \frac{3 - (2 - (9 - (0 - 1)))}{4 \times (7 + (8 - (5 + 6)))} := \frac{3 \times (2 - (9 \times (0 - 1)))}{(4 + (7 - (8 - 5))) \times 6} := \frac{((3 + 2) \times (9 - 0)) - 1}{4 \times (7 + (8 - (5 - 6)))} := \frac{(3^2) + (90 \times 1)}{(4 + (7 + (8 + 5))) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{3 + ((2 \times (9 - 0)) + 1)}{((4 - 7) \times 8) + 56} := \frac{329 - (0 - 1)}{4 \times ((7 + (8 + 5)) \times 6)} := \frac{(3 \times (2 + 90)) - 1}{4 + ((78 \times 5) + 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{32970}{46158} &:= \frac{(3 + 2) \times (9 - (7 - 0))}{4 + (6 + (1 - (5 - 8)))} := \frac{32 - (9 - (7 - 0))}{4 + (6 - ((1 - 5) \times 8))} := \frac{3 + (2 \times (9 + (7 - 0)))}{4 + (6 - (1 - (5 \times 8)))} := \frac{(3 \times (2 + 9)) + (7 - 0)}{4 - (6 - (1 \times 58))} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times ((2 \times 9) + (7 - 0))}{4 + (61 + (5 \times 8))} := \frac{3 - (2 - (9 + 70))}{(4 + (6 - (1 - 5))) \times 8} := \frac{32 + (9 \times (7 - 0))}{((4 \times 6) + 1) \times 5 + 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{34187}{92506} &:= \frac{(3^4 - 1^8) + 7}{92 - (5 \times (0 \times 6))} := \frac{34 + 187}{92 + 506} := \frac{3 \times (((4 - 1) \times 8) - 7)}{(9 - (2^5)) \times (0 - 6)} := \frac{34 \times (18 - 7)}{92 \times (5 - (0 - 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(3^4) \times 187}{(9^2) \times 506} := \frac{(3 + 4) \times 187}{(9 - 2) \times 506} := \frac{34 \times (1 \times (8 \times 7))}{92 \times (50 + 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{34506}{81792} &:= \frac{3^{4+5-06}}{8 \times ((1^7) + (9-2))} := \frac{34+506}{8 \times ((1+79) \times 2)} := \frac{(3 \times (4 \times (5-0))) - 6}{8 \times ((17-9) \times 2)} := \frac{3 \times (45 - (0 \times 6))}{(81+79) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times ((4+50) \times 6)}{(8+1) \times ((7+9)^2)} := \frac{3^{4-5+06}}{8+(1+(7 \times (9^2)))} := \frac{3^{4-5 \times 0 \times 6}}{8 \times (17+(9-2))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{35640}{81972} &:= \frac{3+(5+(6-(4-0)))}{8+(1+(9+(7-2)))} := \frac{3 \times (5 \times (6-(4-0)))}{8+(1 \times ((9 \times 7)-2))} := \frac{35 \times (6-(4-0))}{(8 \times 19)+(7+2)} := \frac{(3+(5-6)) \times 40}{8 \times (1 \times (9+(7 \times 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(3-(5-6)) \times 40}{8 \times (1+(9 \times (7-2)))} := \frac{35 \times (6+(4-0))}{819-(7 \times 2)} := \frac{3 \times (5 \times (6 \times (4-0)))}{819+(7+2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{36045}{72891} &:= \frac{3 \times (6-(0-(4+5)))}{(7+(2-8)) \times 91} := \frac{3 \times (6 \times ((0 \times 4)+5))}{7 \times ((2 \times 8)+(9+1))} := \frac{3 \times (60 \times (4 \times 5))}{728 \times (9+1)} := \frac{(3-(6 \times (0-4))) \times 5}{7+((2^8)+(9+1))} \\ &:= \frac{360 \times (4+5)}{728 \times (9 \times 1)} := \frac{3 \times (60+45)}{7 \times (2+(89 \times 1))} := \frac{(3+(6-0)) \times 45}{728+91} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{37206}{91584} &:= \frac{(3 \times 7)-(2-(0-6))}{(9 \times (1-(5-8))) - 4} := \frac{((3+7) \times (2-0))+6}{9+(1+(58-4))} := \frac{3+(7^{2-0 \times 6})}{(9+(15+8)) \times 4} := \frac{3+(7+(20 \times 6))}{(9+(1^5)) \times (8 \times 4)} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (72-(0-6))}{(9+1) \times 58 - 4} := \frac{37+(2-(0 \times 6))}{(9+15) \times (8-4)} := \frac{(3+(7^2+0)) \times 6}{(9+15) \times (8 \times 4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{37518}{49062} &:= \frac{3+(7-(5-(1 \times 8)))}{4+(9-(0-(6-2)))} := \frac{(3 \times 7)+(5 \times (1^8))}{4+((9-(0-6)) \times 2)} := \frac{3 \times (7+(5+(1^8)))}{49-((0 \times 6)-2)} := \frac{(3-7) \times (5-18)}{4 \times (9-(0-(6+2)))} \\ &:= \frac{3+(75 \times (1^8))}{4+(90+(6+2))} := \frac{((3 \times (7 \times 5))-1) \times 8}{(4+(90 \times 6)) \times 2} := \frac{3 \times ((7+(5+1)) \times 8)}{4 \times (90+(6 \times 2))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{39487}{62051} &:= \frac{(3 \times (9-4))-(8-7)}{6+(2^{05-1})} := \frac{3-(9-(48-7))}{6-(2+(0-51))} := \frac{3 \times (9+(4+(8-7)))}{6 \times ((2 \times (05))+1)} := \frac{(3 \times (9+4))+87}{6 \times ((2^{05})+1)} \\ &:= \frac{3-(9-(48+7))}{6+(20+51)} := \frac{(((3+9) \times 4)+8) \times 7}{620-(5-1)} := \frac{3+(9-(4+(8-7)))}{(6 \times (2-(0 \times 5))) - 1} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{40821}{59376} &:= \frac{4-(0-(8-(2-1)))}{5+(9+(3-(7-6)))} := \frac{4-(0-(8+21))}{(5 \times 9)+(3 \times (7-6))} := \frac{4 \times ((08+(2+1)))}{((5-9) \times 3)+76} := \frac{408+21}{((5 \times 9)+3) \times (7+6)} \\ &:= \frac{40+(82-1)}{(5 \times ((9 \times 3)+7))+6} := \frac{(40 \times 8)-(2-1)}{(5 \times 93)-(7-6)} := \frac{408-(2-1)}{593-(7-6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{41067}{85293} &:= \frac{4+(10+(6-7))}{8+(5+(2+(9+3)))} := \frac{4-((1+(0-6)) \times 7)}{(8+((5 \times 2)+9)) \times 3} := \frac{4 \times (1 \times ((06+7)))}{8+(5+(2+93))} := \frac{(4+(1-0)) \times (6+7)}{(8-(5-2)) \times (9 \times 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4+10) \times (6+7)}{85+293} := \frac{((4+10) \times 6)+7}{8-(5-(2 \times 93))} := \frac{4+(106+7)}{((8-5)^2) \times (9 \times 3)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{43065}{91872} &:= \frac{(4-(3-0)) \times (6 \times 5)}{(9-(1 \times (8-7)))^2} := \frac{4 \times (3 \times ((0 \times 6)+5))}{(9-(1-(8 \times 7))) \times 2} := \frac{(4 \times 30)-(6 \times 5)}{(9+(1 \times 87)) \times 2} := \frac{4 \times (30 \times (6-5))}{(9+((1^8) \times 7))^2} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times 30)+(6 \times 5)}{(9-1) \times (8 \times (7-2))} := \frac{4 \times (30+(6 \times 5))}{(9+(1-8))^{7+2}} := \frac{(4^3+0) \times (6 \times 5)}{(9-(1-(8 \times 7)))^2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{45072}{81693} &:= \frac{(4+(5-(0-7))) \times 2}{8-(1-((6 \times 9)-3))} := \frac{4-(5+(0-(7^2)))}{81-(6-(9+3))} := \frac{4 \times ((5-(0-7))^2)}{(81+6) \times (9+3)} := \frac{4 \times ((5-(0-7)) \times 2)}{8+(169-3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4+(5-(0-7)))^2}{8 \times (1+((6 \times 9)+3))} := \frac{4^{5 \times 0 \times 7+2}}{8-(1 \times (6-(9 \times 3)))} := \frac{4^{5+0 \times 7-2}}{(8 \times 16)-(9+3)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{46190}{78523} &:= \frac{4 + (6 \times (1^9 + 0))}{7 - (8 + (5 - 23))} := \frac{4 \times (6 - (1^9 + 0))}{7 + ((8 \times (5 - 2)) + 3)} := \frac{4 \times (6 + (1 \times (9 - 0)))}{(7 \times (8 + (5 + 2))) - 3} := \frac{(4 \times (6 - 1)) + 90}{7 + ((8 + 52) \times 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (6 \times 1)) \times (9 - 0)}{(7 - (8 - 52)) \times 3} := \frac{4 \times ((6 - 1) \times (9 - 0))}{7 + ((8 + 5) \times 23)} := \frac{4 \times (6 \times (1 + (9 - 0)))}{((7 \times 8) - 5) \times (2^3)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{46782}{53901} &:= \frac{4 + ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 2)}{53 - (9 \times (0 \times 1))} := \frac{4 \times ((6 \times (7 + 8)) + 2)}{53 \times (9 + (0 - 1))} := \frac{46 \times (7 + 82)}{53 \times (90 - 1)} := \frac{(4 \times ((6 + 7) \times 8)) - 2}{53 \times (9 \times 01)} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (6 \times (78 - 2))}{53 \times (9 - (0 - 1))} := \frac{4 \times (6 + (7 + (8 + 2)))}{(5 \times 3) + (90 + 1)} := \frac{46 + 782}{53 + 901} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{48672}{50193} &:= \frac{4 \times (8^{6-7+2})}{5 - (0 - (1 + (9 \times 3)))} := \frac{4 \times (8 \times (6 + (7 + 2)))}{501 - (9 - 3)} := \frac{(4 - (8 - 6))^{7+2}}{501 + (9 \times 3)} := \frac{4 \times ((8 - 6) \times 72)}{501 + 93} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (8 + (6 \times (7 \times 2)))}{5 - (0 - (1 + 93))} := \frac{4 \times (8 - (6 - (7 \times 2)))}{50 + (19 - 3)} := \frac{4 \times (8 + ((6 \times 7) - 2))}{5 - (0 - 193)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{50963}{74128} &:= \frac{5 - (0 - (9 - (6 - 3)))}{7 + (4 - (1 + (2 - 8)))} := \frac{(5 - ((0 \times 9) - 6)) \times 3}{(7 - (4 - (1 + 2))) \times 8} := \frac{50 - (9 - (6 - 3))}{(7 + (4 - (1 + 2))) \times 8} := \frac{5 - (0 - (9 + 63))}{7 \times (4 \times (12 - 8))} \\ &:= \frac{50 + (96 - 3)}{((7 \times (4 \times 1)) - 2) \times 8} := \frac{50 + (9 + (6^3))}{(7 + (41 + 2)) \times 8} := \frac{5 - (0 - 963)}{(7 + 4) \times 128} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{51084}{72369} &:= \frac{(5 - (10 - 8)) \times 4}{7 - (2 + (3 - (6 + 9)))} := \frac{(5 + (1^{08})) \times 4}{7 + ((2 \times (3 + 6)) + 9)} := \frac{(5 - (1 + (0 - 8))) \times 4}{(7 \times (2 + (3 + 6))) - 9} := \frac{5 \times ((1 - (0 - 8)) \times 4)}{((7 \times 2) + 3) \times (6 + 9)} \\ &:= \frac{(5 - (1 - 0)) \times 84}{7 \times (2 - (3 - 69))} := \frac{5 \times ((10 + 8) \times 4)}{7 + ((2^3+6) - 9)} := \frac{(5 + (1 - 0)) \times 84}{((7 + 2)^3) - (6 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{51240}{98637} &:= \frac{5 \times (1 \times (2 \times (4 - 0)))}{9 + (8 + (6 \times (3 + 7)))} := \frac{5 \times (1 \times (2^4 + 0))}{98 + (63 - 7)} := \frac{5 \times (1 \times (24 - 0))}{(9 + (8 \times (6 - 3))) \times 7} := \frac{(5 - (1^2)) \times 40}{(9 - 86) \times (3 - 7)} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times ((1^2) \times 40)}{(9 \times ((8 + 6) \times 3)) + 7} := \frac{(5 + (1 \times 2)) \times 40}{98 + (63 \times 7)} := \frac{5 \times (1 \times (2 \times 40))}{(9 \times 86) + (3 - 7)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{51293}{74608} &:= \frac{5 \times (1 - (2 - (9 + 3)))}{74 + (6 - (0 \times 8))} := \frac{(5 - (1 - (2 \times 9))) \times 3}{(7 \times 4) + (60 + 8)} := \frac{5 + (12 \times (9 - 3))}{7 \times ((4 \times (6 - 0)) - 8)} := \frac{5 - (1 - (2 + 93))}{(7 - 4) \times (6 \times (08))} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times (1 - ((2 - 9) \times 3))}{(7 \times (4 \times (6 - 0))) - 8} := \frac{5 \times (1 + (29 \times 3))}{(74 + (6 - 0)) \times 8} := \frac{5 + (1 + (2 + (9^3)))}{(74 + 60) \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{52734}{91086} &:= \frac{5 - (2 - (7 + (3 \times 4)))}{(9 + 10) \times (8 - 6)} := \frac{5 + (2 \times (7 + (3 + 4)))}{9 - (1 \times (0 - (8 \times 6)))} := \frac{5 - (2 - (7 + 34))}{(9 \times 10) - (8 + 6)} := \frac{5 + (2 \times ((7 \times 3) + 4))}{9 - (1 \times (0 - 86))} \\ &:= \frac{((5^2) \times 7) + 34}{(9 + 10)^{8-6}} := \frac{(5 \times (27 + 3)) + 4}{(9 + 10) \times (8 + 6)} := \frac{((5 \times 27) - 3) \times 4}{(9 + 10) \times (8 \times 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{52893}{76401} &:= \frac{5 + (2^{8-9+3})}{7 + (6 - (4 \times (0 \times 1)))} := \frac{5 + (2 + (8 + (9 + 3)))}{(7 - 6) \times (40 - 1)} := \frac{5 + ((2 \times (8 + 9)) - 3)}{7 + (6 + (40 - 1))} := \frac{5 + (2 \times (8 + (9 + 3)))}{(7 + 6) \times (4 - (0 - 1))} \\ &:= \frac{((5 \times 2) + (8 + 9)) \times 3}{76 + (40 + 1)} := \frac{(52 + 8) \times (9 - 3)}{(7 + 6) \times (40 \times 1)} := \frac{(5 + (2 \times (8 + 9))) \times 3}{(7 \times (6 \times (4 - 0))) + 1} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{53274}{81960} &:= \frac{5 + (3 + (27 + 4))}{8 + (1 - (9 - 60))} := \frac{5 - (3 - (2 + 74))}{8 \times (1 \times (9 + (6 - 0)))} := \frac{5 + (3 + (2 + (7 - 4)))}{(8 \times (1 + 9)) - 60} := \frac{(5 \times 3) + (2 + 74)}{(8 \times (1 + 9)) + 60} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times (3 + (27 - 4))}{8 \times (19 + (6 - 0))} := \frac{(5^3) + (2 \times 74)}{(8 - (1^9)) \times 60} := \frac{((5 \times 3) - 2) \times (7 \times 4)}{8 \times (1 + (9 + 60))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{54901}{86273} &:= \frac{(5 \times 4) + (9 + (0 - 1))}{8 + (6 \times (2 + (7 - 3)))} := \frac{5 + ((4 \times (9 - 0)) + 1)}{8 + (62 - (7 - 3))} := \frac{54 - (9 \times (0 - 1))}{(86 \times 2) - 73} := \frac{5 \times (4 + (9 - (0 - 1)))}{8 + (6 \times ((2 \times 7) + 3))} \\ &:= \frac{5 - (4 - (90 \times 1))}{8 + (62 + 73)} := \frac{5 + (4 + (90 - 1))}{(8 + 6) \times ((2 \times 7) - 3)} := \frac{5 \times ((4 \times (9 - 0)) - 1)}{8 - (6 - 273)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{57312}{60894} &:= \frac{(5 + (7 + (3 + 1))) \times 2}{6 + (0 - (8 - (9 \times 4)))} := \frac{(5 + 7)^{3-1^2}}{60 + (89 + 4)} := \frac{5 \times ((7 - 3) \times (1 + 2))}{(60 + 8) \times (9 - 4)} := \frac{((5 \times 7) - 3) \times 12}{6 \times (((08 + 9) \times 4))} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times (7 \times ((3 + 1)^2))}{608 - (9 + 4)} := \frac{573 + (1 + 2)}{6 \times ((08 + 94))} := \frac{((5 + 7) \times (3 + 1))^2}{(60 + 8) \times (9 \times 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{62730}{81549} &:= \frac{6 + (27 - (3 - 0))}{8 - (1 \times (5 - (4 \times 9)))} := \frac{(6^2) + (7 - (3 - 0))}{8 - (1 \times (5 - 49))} := \frac{6 + ((2 \times 7) + 30)}{((8 + (1 + 5)) \times 4) + 9} := \frac{6 + (2 \times (7 + 30))}{8 \times ((1^5) \times (4 + 9))} \\ &:= \frac{(6^2) \times (7 + (3 - 0))}{((8 \times (1 + 5)) + 4) \times 9} := \frac{6 \times (2 \times (7 + (3 - 0)))}{(8 \times 15) + (4 \times 9)} := \frac{6 \times (2 + (73 - 0))}{(8 + 1) \times (5 \times (4 + 9))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{75036}{98124} &:= \frac{(7 \times (5 - 0)) - (3 + 6)}{9 + (8 + (1 + (2^4)))} := \frac{7 + (50 - (3 \times 6))}{9 + ((8 - 1) \times (2 + 4))} := \frac{7 - (5 \times (0 - (3 + 6)))}{(9 + (8 \times (1^2))) \times 4} := \frac{75 + (0 - (3 - 6))}{(9 + (8 \times 1)) \times (2 + 4)} \\ &:= \frac{7 - ((5 \times (0 \times 3)) - 6)}{9 - (8 - (1 \times (2^4)))} := \frac{7 + ((50 + 3) \times 6)}{(9 + 8) \times (1 + 24)} := \frac{(75 - (0 - 3)) \times 6}{9 \times ((8 \times (1 \times 2)) + 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{75429}{80631} &:= \frac{7 + (5 + ((4 \times 2) + 9))}{(8 \times (0 \times 6)) + 31} := \frac{(7 \times (5 + (4 - 2))) + 9}{(8 + (0 - 6)) \times 31} := \frac{7 + ((5^4 - 2) \times 9)}{8 \times ((0 \times 6) + 31)} := \frac{(7 + (5 + 4)) \times 29}{8 \times ((063 - 1))} \\ &:= \frac{754 - 29}{806 - 31} := \frac{(7 + (5 \times (4^2))) \times 9}{806 + 31} := \frac{(7 + 5) \times (4 \times 29)}{8 \times ((06 \times 31))} \end{aligned}$$

• **Four Digit's Numerator**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1098}{243756} &:= \frac{((1 + 09) \times 8)}{((2^4) \times (37 \times (5 \times 6)))} := \frac{((1^{09}) \times 8)}{((2^4) \times (3 \times (7 + (5 \times 6))))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 \times 8)))}{(((2 + 4)^3) \times 75) + 6} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 - 8)))}{(((2 \times 43) - (7 + 5)) \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (0 \times 98))}{(2 + (4 + (3 \times ((7 + 5) \times 6))))} := \frac{(10 + (9 + 8))}{((2^4) \times 375) - 6} := \frac{(10 + (9 - 8))}{((2 + (4^3)) \times (7 + (5 \times 6)))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{3078}{124659} &:= \frac{3 + 07 - 8}{1 + 2 \times 4 \times (6 - 5 + 9)} := \frac{3 - 07 + 8}{(1 + 2 + 4 + 6 + 5) \times 9} := \frac{3 \times 0 \times 7 + 8}{1 \times ((2 + 4 + 6 \times 5) \times 9)} := \frac{3 + 07 + 8}{1 \times 24 \times 6 \times 5 + 9} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times 07 \times 8}{(1 + 2)^4 \times 6 \times (5 + 9)} := \frac{(30 - 7) \times 8}{12 \times (4 + 65) \times 9} := \frac{(3 + 07) \times 8}{(1 + 2) \times 4 \times 6 \times 5 \times 9} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{3196}{457028} &:= \frac{((3 - (1^9))^6)}{((4 + (570 \times 2)) \times 8)} := \frac{(3 - ((1^9) - 6))}{((4 \times (5 \times 70)) - (2^8))} := \frac{(3 \times (1 \times (9 - 6)))}{((4^5) + (7 - (0 - (2^8))))} := \frac{(3 \times (1^{96}))}{(4 + (5 - (70 \times (2 - 8))))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (1 - (9 - 6)))}{(45 + (70 + 28))} := \frac{(3 + (1^{96}))}{((4 \times (5 + (70 \times 2))) - 8)} := \frac{(3 + (1 + (9 - 6)))}{((4^5) - (7 - (0 - (2 \times 8))))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{3276}{149058} &:= \frac{(3^2) - (7 - 6)}{(1 \times (4 - (9 \times (0 - (5 \times 8)))))} := \frac{((3^2) + (7 - 6))}{(1 - (4 - ((90 \times 5) + 8)))} := \frac{(3 - (2 - (7 + 6)))}{(1 \times (49 \times (0 + (5 + 8))))} := \frac{(3 - (2 - (7 - 6)))}{(1 \times (4 + (90 + (5 - 8))))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (2 - (7 - 6)))}{((1 + (4 + (9 - 0))) \times (5 + 8))} := \frac{(3 + (27 + 6))}{(14 \times (9 \times (0 + (5 + 8))))} := \frac{(32 + 76)}{(1 + (4905 + 8))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3295}{168704} := \frac{(((3^2) + 9) \times 5)}{(16 \times (8 + (70 \times 4)))} := \frac{((3 \times 2) + (9 - 5))}{((16 - 8)^{7-04})} := \frac{((3 + (2 + 9)) \times 5)}{(16 \times (8 \times (7 \times (0 + 4))))} := \frac{((3 + 29) \times 5)}{(16 \times (8^{7-04}))} \\ := \frac{((3 - 2) \times (9 \times 5))}{((16 + (8 \times 70)) \times 4)} := \frac{(3 \times ((2 + 9) \times 5))}{(16 \times (8 \times (70 - 4)))} := \frac{(3 \times (2 \times (9 \times 5)))}{((16 + 8)^{7-04})}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3429}{150876} := \frac{((3 - (4 - 2)) \times 9)}{((1 + (50 + (8 + 7))) \times 6)} := \frac{((3 - (4 - 2))^9)}{(1 + (50 - (8 - (7 - 6))))} := \frac{(3 \times ((4 \times 2) + 9))}{((150 \times (8 + 7)) - 6)} := \frac{(3 \times (4 + 29))}{(1 \times ((50 \times 87) + 6))} \\ := \frac{(3 + ((4 \times 2) - 9))}{(150 - ((8 \times 7) + 6))} := \frac{(3 + (4 + (2 \times 9)))}{(((150 + 8) \times 7) - 6)} := \frac{(3 + (4 + 29))}{(1508 + 76)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3618}{240597} := \frac{(3 - (6 - (1 + 8)))}{((2 - (4 + (0 - 59))) \times 7)} := \frac{(3 - (6 + (1 - 8)))}{(2 - (4 \times (0 - (59 + 7))))} := \frac{(3 \times (6 \times (1^8)))}{((24 + (0 - 5)) \times (9 \times 7))} := \frac{(3 + (6 - (1^8)))}{(((2 \times 40) + (5 - 9)) \times 7)} \\ := \frac{(3 + (6 - (1 - 8)))}{((2 - 40) \times ((5 - 9) \times 7))} := \frac{(3 + (6 + (1 - 8)))}{((2 \times (4 - (0 - 59))) + 7)} := \frac{(36 + (1 \times 8))}{(2 \times (((40 \times 5) + 9) \times 7))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4086}{312579} := \frac{(4 - ((0 \times 8) - 6))}{((3 \times (1 + 257)) - 9)} := \frac{(4 - (0 - (8 - 6)))}{((3 - (1 - ((2 + 5) \times 7))) \times 9)} := \frac{(4 - (0 \times 86))}{((3 - (1 - (25 + 7))) \times 9)} := \frac{(4 \times ((0 \times 8) + 6))}{((3 \times (1 + 2)) \times (5 + (7 \times 9)))} \\ := \frac{(4 \times (0 + (8 - 6)))}{(((3 \times (1 \times 25)) - 7) \times 9)} := \frac{(4 + (0 - (8 - 6)))}{(3 \times (1 + (2 + (57 - 9))))} := \frac{(40 + (8 - 6))}{(3 \times ((12 + 5) \times (7 \times 9)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4156}{238970} := \frac{((4 \times (1 \times 5)) + 6)}{(23 \times ((8 \times 9) - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 - (1 + (5 - 6)))}{(23 \times (8 + (9 - (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 \times ((1^5) + 6))}{(((2 \times 3) + (8 + 9)) \times 70)} := \frac{(4 \times (1 \times 56))}{(2 \times ((3 + 89) \times 70))} \\ := \frac{(4 \times (1 - (5 - 6)))}{(23 + (897 - 0))} := \frac{(4 + (1 - (5 - 6)))}{((2 + 3) \times (8 - (9 - 70)))} := \frac{(41 - (5 - 6))}{(23 \times (8 + (97 - 0)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4178}{259036} := \frac{((4 - 1) \times (7 + 8))}{(((2^5) \times (90 - 3)) + 6)} := \frac{((41 \times 7) - 8)}{(((2^5) \times 90) + 3) \times 6} := \frac{(4 - (1 - (7 - 8)))}{(2 \times (59 + (0 - (3 - 6))))} := \frac{(4 \times (17 - 8))}{(((25 \times 90) - (3 \times 6))} \\ := \frac{(4 + ((1^7) \times 8))}{(2 \times ((59 - (0 - 3)) \times 6))} := \frac{(4 + (1 - (7 - 8)))}{((2 + (5 \times (9 - (0 - 3)))) \times 6)} := \frac{(4 + (1 \times (7 - 8)))}{(((2 \times (5 + (9 - 0))) + 3) \times 6)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4509}{186372} := \frac{((4 + 50) \times 9)}{((1 + 8) \times (6 \times 372))} := \frac{(4 + (5 - (0 \times 9)))}{((1^{86}) \times 372)} := \frac{(4 + (5 - (0 - 9)))}{(1 \times ((8 - 6) \times 372))} := \frac{(4 + (50 + 9))}{(((1^8) + 6) \times 372)} \\ := \frac{(45 - (0 - 9))}{(18 \times ((6 \times (3 \times 7)) - 2))} := \frac{(45 + (0 - 9))}{(186 \times (3 + (7 - 2)))} := \frac{(450 - 9)}{((1 + (8 \times 6)) \times 372)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4527}{316890} := \frac{((4 - (5 - 2))^7)}{(3 + (1 - (6 - (8 \times (9 - 0)))))} := \frac{((4 \times (5 + 2)) + 7)}{((31 - 6) \times (8 + 90))} := \frac{(4 \times ((5^2) - 7))}{(((3 \times 16) + 8) \times 90)} := \frac{(4 + (5 - (2 - 7)))}{(((3 + (1 + 6)) \times (8 + 90))} \\ := \frac{(4 + (5 + 27))}{((3 - 1) \times ((6 + 8) \times 90))} := \frac{(45 - (2 \times 7))}{((3 \times (1 + 6)) - (8 + (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(45 + (2 + 7))}{(3 \times (1 \times ((6 + 8) \times 90)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4536}{192780} := \frac{((4 \times (5 - 3)) + 6)}{(1 - (9 \times ((2 \times 7) - 80)))} := \frac{((4^{5-3}) + 6)}{(1 \times (927 + (8 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 - (5 + (3 - 6)))}{(1 + (9 + (2 - (7 - 80))))} := \frac{(4 \times (5 - (3 - 6)))}{((1 + 9) \times ((2^7) + (8 - 0)))} \\ := \frac{(4^{5+3-6})}{(1 \times ((92 - 7) \times (8 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 + (5 \times 36))}{((1 + 9) \times (2 + 780))} := \frac{(4 + (5 + (3 - 6)))}{((19 - 2) \times (7 + (8 - 0)))}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4617}{350892} &:= \frac{((4 \times 6) - 17)}{((3^5 + 0) + ((8 + 9)^2))} := \frac{(4 - (6 + (1 - 7)))}{((3 \times (5 - 0)) + ((8 + 9)^2))} := \frac{(4 - (6 - 17))}{(3 \times (((50 - 8) \times 9) + 2))} := \frac{(4 + (6 - (1 \times 7)))}{(3 \times (50 + (8 + (9 \times 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (6 - (1^7)))}{(3 \times (50 + (89 \times 2)))} := \frac{(4 + (6 - (1 + 7)))}{(3 + (5 - (0 - (8 \times (9 \times 2)))))} := \frac{(4 + (6 + (1 \times 7)))}{((3 \times (50 \times 8)) + 92)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4671}{389250} &:= \frac{((4 + 6) \times (7 - 1))}{((3 + (8 + 9)) \times 250)} := \frac{(4 - (6 - (7 + 1)))}{((3 + (8 - 9)) \times 250)} := \frac{(4 + ((6 \times 7) - 1))}{(((3 \times 8) - 9) \times 250)} := \frac{(4 + (6 - (7 \times 1)))}{((3 \times (8 + 92)) - 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (6 + (7 + 1)))}{(3 \times ((8 + 92) \times (5 - 0)))} := \frac{(46 \times (7 - 1))}{((3 + 89) \times 250)} := \frac{(46 + (7 + 1))}{((3 + (89 - 2)) \times 50)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4761}{328509} &:= \frac{((4 \times (7 \times 6)) - 1)}{(3 - ((2^8) \times (5 \times (0 - 9))))} := \frac{((4 \times (7 + 6)) - 1)}{((3^2) \times ((8 \times 50) - 9))} := \frac{((4 \times 7) + (6 \times 1))}{(3 \times (2 \times ((8 \times 50) - 9)))} := \frac{(4 - (7 - (6 \times 1)))}{(3 \times (2 + (8 + (50 + 9))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (7 - (6 - 1)))}{(3 + ((2 + (8 + (5 - 0))) \times 9))} := \frac{(4 + (7 - (6 \times 1)))}{(3 - ((2 - (8 \times (5 - 0))) \times 9))} := \frac{(4 + (7 - (6 - 1)))}{(3 + (2 + ((8 \times 50) + 9)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5032}{198764} &:= \frac{((5 - (0 - 3)) \times 2)}{(1 - (9 - (8 \times (76 + 4))))} := \frac{((5 \times (0 \times 3)) + 2)}{(19 + (8 + ((7 + 6) \times 4)))} := \frac{(5 - (0 - (3 + 2)))}{(1 + (((9 + (8 \times 7)) \times 6) + 4))} := \frac{(5 - (0 - (3 - 2)))}{(1 - ((9 + (8 - 76)) \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (0 - (3 - 2)))}{((1 - (9 - 87)) \times (6 - 4))} := \frac{(50 \times (3 - 2))}{(1 + (987 \times (6 - 4)))} := \frac{(50 - 32)}{(1 \times (9 \times (8 + (7 + 64))))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5169}{320478} &:= \frac{(5 - ((1^6)^9))}{(((3 \times (2 \times (0 + 4))) + 7) \times 8)} := \frac{(5 - (1 - (6 - 9)))}{((3 \times (2 - (0 \times 4))) + (7 \times 8))} := \frac{(5 - (1 \times (6 - 9)))}{((3 \times ((20 + 4) \times 7)) - 8)} := \frac{(5 \times (1 - (6 - 9)))}{(((3 \times (2 - 0))^4) - (7 \times 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + ((1^6)^9))}{((3 \times 20) + (4 \times 78))} := \frac{(5 + (1 + (6 - 9)))}{(3 \times (2 - (0 - (4 \times (7 + 8)))))} := \frac{(5 + (16 - 9))}{((3^{2+04}) + (7 + 8))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5283}{406791} &:= \frac{(((5 \times 2) + 8) \times 3)}{((4^{06}) + ((7 \times 9) - 1))} := \frac{(((5 \times 2) - 8) \times 3)}{(406 + (7 \times (9 - 1)))} := \frac{((5 \times 2) - (8 - 3))}{(((4 \times (0 + (6 \times (7 + 9)))) + 1)} := \frac{((5^2) - (8 \times 3))}{(4 + (0 - (6 - (79 \times 1))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 - ((2 - 8) \times 3))}{((40 \times (6 \times 7)) + 91)} := \frac{(5 + (2 - (8 - 3)))}{(((4 - (0 - (6 + 7))) \times 9) + 1)} := \frac{(5 + (2 \times (8 \times 3)))}{((4^{06}) - (7 + (9 - 1)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5643}{127908} &:= \frac{((5 + (6 - 4)) \times 3)}{((1 + 27) \times (9 - (0 - 8)))} := \frac{(5 - (6 - (4^3)))}{(12 \times (7 \times (9 - (0 - 8))))} := \frac{(5 - (6 - (4 + 3)))}{(((1 - (2 + (7 + 9))) \times (0 - 8))} := \frac{(5 - (6 - 43))}{(1 \times (((2^7) - (9 - 0)) \times 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times (6 \times (4 - 3)))}{(1 \times ((2 - (7 - 90)) \times 8))} := \frac{(5 + (6 + (4 + 3)))}{((12 - (7 \times 9)) \times (0 - 8))} := \frac{(5 + (6 + (4 - 3)))}{(1 + (279 + (0 - 8)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5643}{208791} &:= \frac{((5 \times 6) + 43)}{((20 \times ((8 + 7) \times 9)) + 1)} := \frac{(5 - (6 - (4 + 3)))}{((20 \times 8) + ((7 \times 9) - 1))} := \frac{(5 \times (6 \times (4 - 3)))}{(((20 \times (8 \times 7)) - (9 + 1))} := \frac{(5 + ((6 \times 4) - 3))}{(((20 + 87) \times 9) - 1)} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + ((6 - 4)^3))}{((20 \times (8 + (7 + 9))) + 1)} := \frac{(5 + (6 - (4 + 3)))}{(20 + (8 \times (7 + (9 \times 1))))} := \frac{(5 + (6 \times (4 + 3)))}{((20 \times (8 + 79)) - 1)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5697}{108243} &:= \frac{5 - (6 - (9 - 7))}{1 - (0 - (8 - (2 - (4 \times 3))))} := \frac{5 + (6 - (9 - 7))}{(1 - (0 - 8)) \times ((2^4) + 3)} := \frac{5 - (6 - (9 + 7))}{((10 + 8) \times (2^4)) - 3} := \frac{5 + (6 \times (9 - 7))}{(10 \times (8 + 24)) + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{5 + 6 + 9 + 7}{1 + 08^2 + 4 - 3} := \frac{5 \times (6 + (9 - 7))}{10 \times ((8^2) + (4 \times 3))} := \frac{5 + (6 + 97)}{108 \times ((2^4) + 3)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5832}{176904} &:= \frac{(5 - (8 - (3 \times 2)))}{(((1^7) + 6) \times (9 - (0 - 4)))} := \frac{(5 - (8 - (3^2)))}{((1 + (7 + 6)) \times (9 - (0 - 4)))} := \frac{(5 \times (8 - (3 + 2)))}{(1 \times (7 \times (69 + (0 - 4))))} := \frac{(5 \times (8 \times (3 \times 2)))}{((1 + 7) \times (6 + 904))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + ((8 - 3)^2))}{((1^7) \times (6 + 904))} := \frac{(5 + (8 - (3 - 2)))}{(1 \times ((7 - (6 - 90)) \times 4))} := \frac{(5 + (8 + (3 + 2)))}{(1 \times (7 \times (6 \times (9 - (0 - 4))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{5841}{327096} &:= \frac{(5 - (8 - (4 \times 1)))}{(3 - (2 - (70 - (9 + 6))))} := \frac{(5 - (8 - (4 + 1)))}{((3^2) + (7 - (0 - 96)))} := \frac{(5 \times (8 - (4 + 1)))}{((3 + ((2^7 + 0) + 9)) \times 6)} := \frac{(5 \times (8 \times (4 - 1)))}{(32 \times (70 \times (9 - 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 \times (8 + (4 \times 1)))}{(32 \times (7 \times (0 + (9 + 6))))} := \frac{(5 + ((8 \times 4) - 1))}{((327 - (0 - 9)) \times 6)} := \frac{(5 + (8 - (4 \times 1)))}{(3 \times (2 + (70 + 96)))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5967}{318240} &:= \frac{((5 \times 9) - (6 \times 7))}{((3 + (18^2)) \times 40)} := \frac{(5 - (9 - (6 + 7)))}{((3 - (1 - (8 + 2))) \times 40)} := \frac{(5 - (9 - 67))}{((3 - (1 - 82)) \times 40)} := \frac{(5 + (9 - (6 - 7)))}{((3 + (1 + (8 \times 2))) \times 40)} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + (9 + 67))}{(3 \times (18 \times (2 \times 40)))} := \frac{(5 + (96 + 7))}{(3 \times (1 \times (8 \times 240)))} := \frac{(59 + (6 + 7))}{((3 - 1) \times (8 \times 240))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{6102}{357984} &:= \frac{(6 - (1 - (0 - 2)))}{(3 + (5 - ((7 - 9) \times 84)))} := \frac{(6 \times (1 - (0 - 2)))}{(3 \times (((5 \times (7 + 9)) + 8) \times 4))} := \frac{(6 \times (10 + 2))}{(3 \times (((5 \times 7) + 9) \times (8 \times 4)))} := \frac{(6 \times (1 \times (0 + 2)))}{((3 + (5 \times (7 + 98))) \times 4)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times (1^{02}))}{((3 \times (((5 + 7) \times 9) + 8)) + 4)} := \frac{(6 + (1 - (0 - 2)))}{((3 + (57 + (9 \times 8))) \times 4)} := \frac{(6 + 102)}{(3 \times ((57 + 9) \times (8 \times 4)))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{6489}{253071} &:= \frac{(6 - (4 - (8 + 9)))}{((2 \times (53 \times (0 + 7))) - 1)} := \frac{(6 - (4 + (8 - 9)))}{(2 + (5 \times (30 - (7 \times 1))))} := \frac{(6 + ((4 \times 8) - 9))}{((2 \times 530) + 71)} := \frac{(6 + (4 - (8 - 9)))}{((2 \times (5 + (30 \times 7))) - 1)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + (4 \times (8 - 9)))}{((2 \times (5 + 30)) + (7 + 1))} := \frac{(6 + (4 + (8 + 9)))}{(2 + ((5 \times (30 \times 7)) + 1))} := \frac{(6 + (4 + (8 - 9)))}{(((2 + 5)^3 + 0) + (7 + 1))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{6492}{178530} &:= \frac{((6 + (4 - 9)) \times 2)}{(1 - (7 - (8 + (53 - 0))))} := \frac{((6 + 4) \times (9 - 2))}{((1 - 78) \times (5 - 30))} := \frac{((6 - 4) \times (9 - 2))}{(1 \times (7 \times (85 - 30)))} := \frac{(6 - ((4 - 9) \times 2))}{((1 + 7) \times (85 - 30))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times (4 + (9 - 2)))}{(1785 + 30)} := \frac{(6 + (4 \times (9 + 2)))}{((1 - (7 \times 8)) \times (5 - 30))} := \frac{(6 + (4 \times (9 - 2)))}{(17 \times (85 - 30))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{7086}{152349} &:= \frac{((7 \times (0 \times 8)) + 6)}{(1 \times ((5 \times (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + 9))} := \frac{((7 \times (0 + 8)) - 6)}{(1 \times ((5^2) \times (34 + 9)))} := \frac{(7 \times ((0 \times 8) + 6))}{(((15^2) + 3) \times 4 - 9)} := \frac{(7 \times (0 + (8 + 6)))}{((1^5) + (234 \times 9))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 \times (0 + (8 - 6)))}{(1 \times ((5 + 2) \times (34 + 9)))} := \frac{(70 - (8 \times 6))}{(((1 + (5 \times 23)) \times 4) + 9)} := \frac{(70 + (8 - 6))}{(((1 + 5)^2) \times (34 + 9))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{7209}{134568} &:= \frac{((7 - (2 - 0)) \times 9)}{(1 \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 8)))))} := \frac{(7 \times (2 \times (0 + 9)))}{((1 + (3 + 45)) \times (6 \times 8))} := \frac{(7 + (2 - (0 \times 9)))}{(1 \times ((3 + (4 + 5)) \times (6 + 8)))} := \frac{(7 + (2 - (0 - 9)))}{((1 - (3 - (4 \times (5 + 6)))) \times 8)} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + (20 + 9))}{(1 \times ((3 + 45) \times (6 + 8)))} := \frac{(7 + 209)}{((13 - 4) \times (56 \times 8))} := \frac{(72 - (0 \times 9))}{(1 \times (3 \times (456 - 8)))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{7218}{364509} &:= \frac{((7 + (2 \times 1)) \times 8)}{(3645 + (0 - 9))} := \frac{(7 \times (2 + 18))}{(((3 + 6)^4) + 509)} := \frac{(7 + (2 + (1 + 8)))}{((3^6) - (4 \times (5 \times (0 - 9))))} := \frac{(7 + (2 + (1 - 8)))}{(((3 \times 6) + 4) \times (5 - 0)) - 9)} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + (21 + 8))}{((3 \times 6) + (4 \times (50 \times 9)))} := \frac{72 + 18}{36 + 4509} := \frac{72 - 18}{3 + 6 \times (4 + 50 \times 9)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{7408}{125936} &:= \frac{((7 - (4 - 0)) \times 8)}{(1 + (2 + (5 \times (9 \times (3 + 6)))))} := \frac{((7 - (4 - 0))^8)}{((12 + 5) \times (9 \times (3^6)))} := \frac{((7 \times (4 - 0)) + 8)}{(1 - ((2 \times 59) - (3^6)))} := \frac{(7 - (4 \times (0 \times 8)))}{(1 + ((2 \times (59 - 3)) + 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 - (4 + (0 - 8)))}{(1 + (((2 \times (5 + 9)) + 3) \times 6))} := \frac{(7 + (4 + (0 - 8)))}{(1 - ((2 \times (5 - (9 \times 3))) - 6))} := \frac{(74 + (0 - 8))}{((125 \times 9) + (3 - 6))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{7956}{310284} &:= \frac{((7 \times 9) - (5 + 6))}{(((3 + 10)^2) \times (8 + 4))} := \frac{((7 \times 9) - 56)}{(3 + (10 + ((2^8) + 4)))} := \frac{((7 - 9) \times (5 - 6))}{((3 \times (1 \times (0 - 2))) + 84)} := \frac{(7 - (9 \times (5 - 6)))}{((310 \times 2) + (8 - 4))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 \times (9 + (5 - 6)))}{((3 + 10) \times (2 \times 84))} := \frac{(7 + (9 - (5 + 6)))}{(3 \times (1 - (0 - (2 \times (8 \times 4)))))} := \frac{(7 + (95 - 6))}{((310 + 2) \times (8 + 4))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{7956}{342108} &:= \frac{((7 \times (9 - 5)) + 6)}{(((3 + 4) \times 210) - 8)} := \frac{((7 - 9) \times (5 - 6))}{((3 \times ((4^2) + 10)) + 8)} := \frac{(7 - (9 - (5 + 6)))}{(3 + (4 \times ((2 + 10) \times 8)))} := \frac{(7 - (9 \times (5 - 6)))}{((34 \times (2 \times 10)) + 8)} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + (9 - (5 + 6)))}{(3 - (4 - (2 \times 108)))} := \frac{(7 + (9 - (5 - 6)))}{((3^4 + 2) + (10 - 8))} := \frac{(79 - (5 \times 6))}{(3 - (4 - 2108))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{7965}{108324} &:= \frac{7+(9-(6+5))}{1 \times (((08+(3^2)) \times 4))} := \frac{7+(9-(6-5))}{(10+(8 \times 3)) \times (2+4)} := \frac{(7-(9-6)) \times 5}{(10+(8 \times 3)) \times (2 \times 4)} := \frac{(7+(9-6)) \times 5}{10 \times ((8+(3^2)) \times 4)} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (9+(6-5))}{((10 \times (8 \times 3))-2) \times 4} := \frac{(7 \times (9+6))-5}{10 \times (8+(32 \times 4))} := \frac{7+((9-6)^5)}{10 \times ((83+2) \times 4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8130}{247965} &:= \frac{(8-(1-(3-0)))}{(2-((4-7) \times (96+5)))} := \frac{(8-(1+(3-0)))}{(24+(7+(96-5)))} := \frac{(8 \times (1 \times 30))}{(24 \times ((7+(9 \times 6)) \times 5))} := \frac{(8 \times (1+(3-0)))}{(2 \times ((47 \times 9)+65))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 \times (1^3+0))}{(2 \times (47+((9+6) \times 5)))} := \frac{(8+(1-(3-0)))}{((2 \times (4+(79+6)))+5)} := \frac{(8+(1+(3-0)))}{(2+(4 \times (((7+9) \times 6)-5)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8130}{296745} &:= \frac{(8-(1-(3-0)))}{((2-(9-(6+74))) \times 5)} := \frac{(8-(1+(3-0)))}{(2 \times (96-((7 \times 4)-5)))} := \frac{(8 \times (1 \times (3-0)))}{((2^9)-(6-(74 \times 5)))} := \frac{(8 \times (1^3+0))}{(29+((67 \times 4)-5))} \\ &:= \frac{(8+(1-(3-0)))}{((2 \times (96+(7+4)))+5)} := \frac{(8+(1 \times 30))}{(2+((9+(67 \times 4)) \times 5))} := \frac{(81+(3-0))}{(((2^9) \times 6)-(7+(4-5)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8230}{176945} &:= \frac{((8 \times 2)^3+0)}{((1+(76+9)) \times (4^5))} := \frac{((8-2) \times (3-0))}{(1 \times ((7 \times (6 \times 9))+(4+5)))} := \frac{((8-2) \times 30)}{((1+(769+4)) \times 5)} := \frac{(8-(2 \times (3-0)))}{(1+(7 \times (6-(9-(4+5))))))} \\ &:= \frac{(8-(2-30))}{((1+(76+9)) \times (4+5))} := \frac{(8+(2 \times (3-0)))}{((1^7)+((6+9) \times (4 \times 5)))} := \frac{(8+(2^3+0))}{(1+(7 \times (69-(4 \times 5))))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8274}{153069} &:= \frac{((8 \times (2 \times 7))-4)}{(((1+5)^3+0)+6) \times 9} := \frac{((8 \times 2)+74)}{(1 \times ((5+(30 \times 6)) \times 9))} := \frac{((8+(2-7)) \times 4)}{(1+(5+((30-6) \times 9)))} := \frac{((8-2)^{7-4})}{(((15 \times 30)-6) \times 9)} \\ &:= \frac{(8-(2 \times (7-4)))}{(1-((5-(3-(0-6))) \times 9))} := \frac{(8+((2 \times 7)-4))}{(((1+(53-0)) \times 6)+9)} := \frac{(82-74)}{(1+((5 \times 30)+(6-9)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8703}{461259} &:= \frac{((8-(7-0)) \times 3)}{((4 \times (6 \times (1 \times (2+5))))-9)} := \frac{((8 \times (7-0))+3)}{((4+((6+1)^2)) \times 59)} := \frac{((8+(7-0)) \times 3)}{((4+((6+1)^2)) \times (5 \times 9))} := \frac{(8-(7-(0 \times 3)))}{(4+(6-(1 \times (2-(5 \times 9))))))} \\ &:= \frac{(8-(7+(0-3)))}{(4 \times (6+(1 \times (2+(5 \times 9))))))} := \frac{(8+(7-(0-3)))}{((4+(6 \times (12+5))) \times 9)} := \frac{(8+(7+(0-3)))}{(4 \times ((6 \times (1 \times 25))+9))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9540}{173628} &:= \frac{((9 \times 5)+40)}{(1+(7+(3+(6 \times (2^8))))))} := \frac{((9 \times 5)-40)}{(1 \times (7 \times (3-(6-(2 \times 8))))))} := \frac{(9 \times (5 \times 40))}{((1+(((7-3)^6)-2)) \times 8)} := \frac{(9 \times (5+40))}{(1+(7362+8))} \\ &:= \frac{(9+(5-(4-0)))}{(1 \times (7 \times (36-(2+8))))} := \frac{(95+40)}{(1+(((7^3)-(6^2)) \times 8))} := \frac{(95-40)}{(1-((7-3) \times (6-(2^8))))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9632}{174580} &:= \frac{((9 \times (6 \times 3))-2)}{(((1^7)+4) \times 580)} := \frac{(9-(6-(3+2)))}{((17 \times (4+5))-(8-0))} := \frac{(9+(6+(3^2)))}{(1+(7 \times (4+(58-0))))} := \frac{(9+(6+(3-2)))}{(1 \times ((74 \times 5)-80))} \\ &:= \frac{(96 \times (3-2))}{(1 \times ((7-4) \times 580))} := \frac{(96+32)}{((1+(7-4)) \times 580)} := \frac{(96-32)}{((1+(7 \times 4)) \times (5 \times (8-0)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9831}{462057} &:= \frac{((9-8) \times (3-1))}{(4-(6 \times (20-(5 \times 7))))} := \frac{((9-8)^3 \times 1)}{(4+(6+(2-(0-(5 \times 7))))))} := \frac{(9-(8-(3 \times 1)))}{(4 \times (((6+(2-0)) \times 5)+7))} := \frac{(9-(8-(3+1)))}{((4 \times (62+(0-5)))+7)} \\ &:= \frac{(9-(8-(3-1)))}{(4+(((6+20) \times 5)+7))} := \frac{(9+(8-(3 \times 1)))}{((4+(6 \times (20-5))) \times 7)} := \frac{(9+(8-(3+1)))}{(4+((6 \times (20 \times 5))+7))} \end{aligned}$$

3.7 8 Equivalent Blocks

• Five Digit's Numerator

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{12047}{65398} &:= \frac{1 + (2 \times (0 - (4 - 7)))}{6 + ((5 \times 3) + (9 + 8))} := \frac{1 + (2 - (0 - (4 + 7)))}{6 - (5 \times (3 - (9 + 8)))} := \frac{(1 - (2 + (0 - 4))) \times 7}{6 \times (5 - (3 - (9 + 8)))} := \frac{1 - (20 - 47)}{(6 \times ((5 \times 3) + 9)) + 8} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (2 \times ((04 \times 7)))}{(6 + (5 + (3 \times 9))) \times 8} := \frac{(1 + (2 - 0)) \times (4 \times 7)}{((6 \times (5 + 3)) + 9) \times 8} := \frac{(1 - (2 \times (0 - 4))) \times 7}{(6 \times 5) + (39 \times 8)} := \frac{(1 + 204) \times 7}{(6^5) - (3 - (9 + 8))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{12537}{60894} &:= \frac{1 \times (2 - (5 - (3 + 7)))}{6 + (0 - (8 - (9 \times 4)))} := \frac{1 \times (2 + (5 + (3 \times 7)))}{60 + ((8 \times 9) + 4)} := \frac{1 \times ((2 + (5 + 3)) \times 7)}{(60 + 8) \times (9 - 4)} := \frac{1 \times (2 \times (5 + 37))}{6 \times (((08 + 9) \times 4))} \\ &:= \frac{(1^2) \times (5 \times (3 \times 7))}{6 \times ((089 - 4))} := \frac{(1 + (2 + (5 \times 3))) \times 7}{6 \times ((08 + 94))} := \frac{12 \times (5 + 37)}{(60 + 8) \times (9 \times 4)} := \frac{12 \times (5 \times (3 \times 7))}{60 \times (8 + 94)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{12684}{53907} &:= \frac{1 \times (2 \times (6 + (8 - 4)))}{5 - (3 - (90 - 7))} := \frac{1 \times (2^{6-8+4})}{5 + (3 + (9 - (0 \times 7)))} := \frac{1 \times (2 - (6 - (8 \times 4)))}{(5 + (3 + (9 - 0))) \times 7} := \frac{1 \times ((2 \times (6 + 8)) + 4)}{53 + (90 - 7)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (2 + (6 + (8 \times 4)))}{5 \times ((3 \times (9 - 0)) + 7)} := \frac{((1 - (2 - 6)) \times 8) + 4}{((5 - 3) \times 90) + 7} := \frac{(12 - (6 - 8)) \times 4}{(5 - 39) \times (0 - 7)} := \frac{1 \times (2 + (6 + (8 - 4)))}{5 + (39 - (0 - 7))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{12690}{58374} &:= \frac{1 \times (2 - (6 - (9 - 0)))}{(5 \times 8) - ((3 \times 7) - 4)} := \frac{(1^{26}) + (9 - 0)}{5 + (8 + (3 \times (7 + 4)))} := \frac{12 - (6 - (9 - 0))}{5 - (8 \times (3 - (7 + 4)))} := \frac{1 \times (26 + (9 - 0))}{5 + (8 + (37 \times 4))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (2 - 6)) \times (9 - 0)}{((5 + (8 \times 3)) \times 7) + 4} := \frac{1 \times ((2^6) - (9 - 0))}{5 + (8 \times (3 + (7 \times 4)))} := \frac{(1^{26}) \times 90}{(5 \times 8) + 374} := \frac{126 + (9 - 0)}{5 + (8 \times (3 + 74))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{12690}{83754} &:= \frac{(1^{26}) + (9 - 0)}{8 - (3 - (7 + 54))} := \frac{12 - (6 - (9 - 0))}{8 + (37 + 54)} := \frac{(12 - 6) \times 90}{((8^3) \times 7) - (5 \times 4)} := \frac{(1 - (2 - 6)) \times (9 - 0)}{(8 \times 37) + (5 - 4)} \\ &:= \frac{(1^2) - (6 - 90)}{(83 \times 7) - (5 \times 4)} := \frac{((1^2) + 6) \times 90}{(8 + 3) \times (7 \times 54)} := \frac{126 + (9 - 0)}{837 + 54} := \frac{1 - (26 - 90)}{(8 + 3) \times ((7 \times 5) + 4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{13620}{98745} &:= \frac{(1^3) \times (6 - (2 - 0))}{9 + ((8 - 7) \times (4 \times 5))} := \frac{1 - (3 + (6 - 20))}{9 + (87 - (4 + 5))} := \frac{1 + (3 + (6 \times (2 - 0)))}{9 + (87 + (4 \times 5))} := \frac{(1^{36}) \times 20}{(9 - (8 - (7 \times 4))) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times (6 \times (2 - 0)))}{9 \times ((8 \times (7 - 4)) + 5)} := \frac{((1 + 3) \times 6) + 20}{(9 \times (8 + (7 \times 4))) - 5} := \frac{1 - (3 - (62 - 0))}{(98 - (7 + 4)) \times 5} := \frac{1 \times (3 \times (6^2 + 0))}{9 \times (8 + (74 + 5))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14076}{59823} &:= \frac{1 \times (4 - (0 \times 76))}{5 + (9 + (8 - (2 + 3)))} := \frac{14 - ((0 \times 7) - 6)}{5 \times (9 - (8 \times (2 - 3)))} := \frac{(1 - (4 + (0 - 7))) \times 6}{5 + (98 + (2 - 3))} := \frac{((1^4 + 0) + 7) \times 6}{5 + ((98 \times 2) + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (4 \times ((07 + 6)))}{((5 + 9) \times (8 \times 2)) - 3} := \frac{(1 + (4 - (0 - 7))) \times 6}{(59 - 8) \times (2 \times 3)} := \frac{14 \times ((0 \times 7) + 6)}{(59 \times (8 - 2)) + 3} := \frac{1 \times (40 \times (7 - 6))}{5 - ((9 - (8^2)) \times 3)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14520}{98736} &:= \frac{(1^4) \times (5 \times (2 - 0))}{9 - (8 - (73 - 6))} := \frac{1 + (4 + (5 \times (2 - 0)))}{(9 \times (8 + (7 - 3))) - 6} := \frac{1 \times (45 - 20)}{(9 + 8) \times (7 - (3 - 6))} := \frac{(1 - 4) \times (5 - 20)}{((9 \times 8) - (7 \times 3)) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (45 \times (2 - 0))}{9 \times (8 + ((7 + 3) \times 6))} := \frac{1 + (4 + (5 \times 20))}{(9 \times (8 \times (7 + 3))) - 6} := \frac{((1^4) + 5) \times 20}{(9 \times (87 + 3)) + 6} := \frac{1 \times (4 \times (5 \times (2 - 0)))}{(9 + 8) \times (7 + (3 + 6))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14823}{79056} &:= \frac{1 - (4 + (8 - 23))}{(7 \times (9 - 0)) - (5 - 6)} := \frac{1 - (4 - ((8 - 2) \times 3))}{79 + (0 - (5 - 6))} := \frac{1 + (4 + (8 + (2 + 3)))}{(7 + (9 - (0 \times 5))) \times 6} := \frac{1 + (4 + (8 + (2^3)))}{(7 - 9) \times (0 - 56)} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (4 \times (8 \times (2 - 3)))}{(7 + (9 - 0)) \times (5 + 6)} := \frac{1 + (4 + (82 + 3))}{(7 + (9 - 0)) \times (5 \times 6)} := \frac{1 + (4 - (8 - (2 \times 3)))}{7 + (9 - (0 \times 56))} := \frac{((1 + 4)^{8-2}) \times 3}{(7 + (9 - 0)) \times (5^6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{15078}{23694} &:= \frac{1 + (5 + (0 - (7 - 8)))}{2 - (3 + ((6 - 9) \times 4))} := \frac{1 + (5 - ((0 \times 7) - 8))}{(2 \times ((3 \times 6) - 9)) + 4} := \frac{1 + (5 - (0 - (7 + 8)))}{2 + (36 - (9 - 4))} := \frac{1 - ((5 \times (0 - 7)) + 8)}{2 \times (3 + (6 + (9 + 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (50 - (7 + 8))}{2 + (3 + ((6 \times 9) - 4))} := \frac{1 \times (50 + (7 - 8))}{2 - (3 - (6 \times (9 + 4)))} := \frac{(1^5 + 0) \times (7 \times 8)}{(2 \times (3 - 6)) + 94} := \frac{1 + (5 - (0 - 78))}{2 + (36 + 94)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{15687}{49302} &:= \frac{1 \times (5 - (6 - (8 + 7)))}{49 - (3 - (0 - 2))} := \frac{1 \times ((5 + (6 - 8)) \times 7)}{((4 \times 9) - (3 - 0)) \times 2} := \frac{1 \times (5 \times (6 + (8 - 7)))}{(4 \times (9 \times (3 - 0))) + 2} := \frac{1 + (56 - (8 + 7))}{((4 \times 9) + 30) \times 2} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((5 - (6 - 8)) \times 7)}{(4 \times (9 + 30)) - 2} := \frac{(15 - (6 - 8)) \times 7}{(4 \times (93 - 0)) + 2} := \frac{(1^{568}) \times 7}{4 + (9 + (3^{02}))} := \frac{(1 + (56 - 8)) \times 7}{(4 \times (9 \times 30)) - 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{15893}{27640} &:= \frac{1 \times (58 - (9 + 3))}{2 \times ((7 - 6) \times 40)} := \frac{(1 + (5 + (8 + 9))) \times 3}{(2 + (7 - 6)) \times 40} := \frac{1 - (5 - (8 \times (9 + 3)))}{2 \times (76 + (4 - 0))} := \frac{(15 + 8) \times (9 - 3)}{2 - (7 \times (6 - 40))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (5 \times ((8 \times 9) - 3))}{(2 + (7 + 6)) \times 40} := \frac{1 \times (5 \times (89 + 3))}{((2 \times 7) + 6) \times 40} := \frac{15 - (8 - (9^3))}{(2^7) \times (6 + (4 - 0))} := \frac{15 + (8 \times 93)}{(27 + 6) \times 40} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{15930}{46728} &:= \frac{1 \times (5 \times (9 - (3 - 0)))}{4 \times ((6 \times (7 - 2)) - 8)} := \frac{1 + (5 + (9 + 30))}{((4 + 6) \times (7 \times 2)) - 8} := \frac{1 \times ((5 \times 9) + 30)}{(4 + 6) \times ((7 \times 2) + 8)} := \frac{1 + (59 + 30)}{((4 \times 6) + (7 + 2)) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{(15 \times 9) - 30}{4 \times (67 + (2 + 8))} := \frac{(1 - (5 - 9)) \times 30}{(46 + (7 + 2)) \times 8} := \frac{(15 \times 9) + 30}{4 + (6 \times (72 + 8))} := \frac{(1 + 59) \times (3 - 0)}{4 \times (6 \times ((7 \times 2) + 8))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{16038}{49572} &:= \frac{1 \times (6 + (0 - (3 - 8)))}{4 + (((9 - 5) \times 7) + 2)} := \frac{1 \times (60 - 38)}{4 + (9 + (57 - 2))} := \frac{1 - (6 + (0 - 38))}{(49 - (5 - 7)) \times 2} := \frac{1 \times (6 - (0 - 38))}{4 \times (9 + (5 \times (7 - 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (6 \times ((03 + 8)))}{(4 + ((9 + 5) \times 7)) \times 2} := \frac{1 + (60 + 38)}{((49 - 5) \times 7) - 2} := \frac{16 \times ((03 + 8))}{495 + (7^2)} := \frac{160 + 38}{4 \times (9 + ((5 + 7)^2))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{16392}{45078} &:= \frac{1 \times (6 + (3 + (9 - 2)))}{4 - (5 \times ((0 \times 7) - 8))} := \frac{1 \times (6 + (3 + (9 + 2)))}{4 - (5 + (0 - (7 \times 8)))} := \frac{1 + (6 + (3 \times (9 - 2)))}{4 - (5 + (0 - 78))} := \frac{1 + (6 + (3 \times (9 + 2)))}{4 + (50 + (7 \times 8))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (6 + (39 + 2))}{(4 \times (5 \times (07))) - 8} := \frac{1 + (((6 + 3) \times 9) - 2)}{(4 \times (50 + 7)) - 8} := \frac{1 \times ((6 \times (3 \times 9)) + 2)}{450 - (7 - 8)} := \frac{(163 + 9) \times 2}{(4^5 + 0) - 78} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{17380}{29546} &:= \frac{1 + ((7 \times 3) + (8 - 0))}{2 + (95 - 46)} := \frac{(1 + (7 - 3)) \times (8 - 0)}{2 - ((9 - (5 \times 4)) \times 6)} := \frac{1 - ((7 \times 3) - 80)}{((29 - 5) \times 4) + 6} := \frac{(1^73) \times 80}{(2 \times (9 \times 5)) + 46} \\ &:= \frac{17 + (3 + 80)}{2 \times (95 - (4 + 6))} := \frac{(17 + 3) \times (8 - 0)}{2 - ((9 - 54) \times 6)} := \frac{1 - (7 \times (3 - 80))}{2 \times (9 \times (5 + 46))} := \frac{(1^7) \times 380}{2 + ((9 + 5) \times 46)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{18306}{92547} &:= \frac{1 + (8 + (3 - (0 - 6)))}{(9 \times (2 + 5)) + (4 \times 7)} := \frac{(1 + (8 - (3 - 0))) \times 6}{(9 \times (25 - 4)) - 7} := \frac{18 \times (3 - (0 \times 6))}{(((9 - 2) \times 5) + 4) \times 7} := \frac{1 + (83 - (0 - 6))}{(9 + (2 + 54)) \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{(18 + (3 - 0)) \times 6}{(92 - (5 - 4)) \times 7} := \frac{18 \times (3 - (0 - 6))}{(9 + (2 \times 54)) \times 7} := \frac{(1^8) \times 306}{((9 \times 25) - 4) \times 7} := \frac{1 \times (8 \times (3 - (0 - 6)))}{(9 - 2) \times (5 + 47)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{18504}{76329} &:= \frac{1 \times (8^{5-04})}{7 - (6 - (3 + 29))} := \frac{(1 - (8 + 5)) \times (0 - 4)}{(7 + (6 + (3^2))) \times 9} := \frac{(1 + (8 + (5 - 0))) \times 4}{7 \times ((6 - 3) \times (2 + 9))} := \frac{1 \times (8 \times (5 - (0 - 4)))}{(7 - (6 - 32)) \times 9} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (8 - (5 - 0))) \times 4}{76 - (3 - (2 - 9))} := \frac{((1^8) + (5 - 0)) \times 4}{7 + (63 + 29)} := \frac{(1 - 85) \times (0 - 4)}{7 \times (6 \times (3 \times (2 + 9)))} := \frac{1 \times (8 \times 504)}{7 \times ((6^3) \times (2 + 9))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{18734}{50692} &:= \frac{1 - (8 - (7 + 34))}{5 - (0 - (6 + (9^2)))} := \frac{1 \times (8 + (73 + 4))}{5 - (0 - ((6 + 9)^2))} := \frac{1 + (8 \times (7 + (3 \times 4)))}{506 - 92} := \frac{187 + 34}{506 + 92} \\ &:= \frac{(18 \times (7 \times 3)) - 4}{(5 - (0 - 6)) \times 92} := \frac{187 \times (3^4)}{506 \times (9^2)} := \frac{187 \times (3 + 4)}{506 \times (9 - 2)} := \frac{1 \times (8 \times (7 \times 34))}{(50 + 6) \times 92} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{19056}{73842} &:= \frac{1 \times (9 - (0 - (5 - 6)))}{7 - (3 \times (8 - (4^2)))} := \frac{1 + (9 - ((0 \times 5) - 6))}{(7 + (3 \times 8)) \times (4 - 2)} := \frac{1 \times ((9 + (0 - 5)) \times 6)}{(7 \times (3 + 8)) + (4^2)} := \frac{1 + (9 - (0 - (5 \times 6)))}{73 + (84 - 2)} \\ &:= \frac{(1^9 + 0) \times 56}{7 - ((3 - 8) \times 42)} := \frac{1 + (90 - (5 + 6))}{(7 \times ((3 + 8) \times 4)) + 2} := \frac{(1 - 9) \times (0 - (5 + 6))}{(7^3) - (8 - (4 + 2))} := \frac{1 - (9 + (0 - 56))}{(7 + (3 \times 8)) \times (4 + 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{20376}{89145} &:= \frac{2^{03} \times (7 - 6)}{(8 \times (9 - (1 \times 4))) - 5} := \frac{2^{03+7-6}}{(8 + (9 + (1 - 4))) \times 5} := \frac{20 + (3 + (7 - 6))}{(8 + (9 + (1 \times 4))) \times 5} := \frac{20 \times (3 - (7 - 6))}{(8 - (9 \times (1 - 4))) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (3 + 7))) \times 6}{(8 \times ((9 + 1) \times 4)) - 5} := \frac{2 - (0 - (3 \times (7 \times 6)))}{8 \times ((9 + (1 + 4)) \times 5)} := \frac{(2^{-03+7}) \times 6}{((8 \times (9 + 1)) + 4) \times 5} := \frac{2^{0 \times 37+6}}{8 \times (((9 + 1) \times 4) - 5)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{20916}{53784} &:= \frac{2 \times (0 - (9 - 16))}{5 + (3 + (7 \times (8 - 4)))} := \frac{2 \times ((09 - (1 - 6)))}{(5 + ((3 \times 7) - 8)) \times 4} := \frac{(2 + (0 - 9)) \times (1 - 6)}{5 + (3 + (78 + 4))} := \frac{2 + ((0 \times 9) - (1 - 6))}{(5 \times (3 + 7)) - (8 \times 4)} \\ &:= \frac{2 - (0 - (9 \times (1 \times 6)))}{53 + (7 + 84)} := \frac{(20 \times 9) + 16}{(5 + 37) \times (8 + 4)} := \frac{20 \times (9 - (1 - 6))}{(53 + 7) \times (8 + 4)} := \frac{(20 \times (9 - 1)) - 6}{(5 \times ((3 + 7) \times 8)) - 4} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{21740}{36958} &:= \frac{2 \times (1^7 + 4) + 0}{3^{6-9+5} + 8} := \frac{(2 \times (1 + 7)) + (4 - 0)}{3 - (6 - ((9 \times 5) - 8))} := \frac{(2 - (1^7)) \times 40}{(3 \times (6 + (9 + 5))) + 8} := \frac{2 + (1 + (7 + 40))}{3 + (69 + (5 + 8))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times ((1^7) \times 40)}{(36 \times (9 - 5)) - 8} := \frac{(2 + (1^7)) \times 40}{(3 \times 69) + (5 - 8)} := \frac{(2 + (1 \times 7)) \times 40}{(3^6) - (9 \times (5 + 8))} := \frac{(2 + (1 + 7)) \times 40}{(3^6) + (9 - 58)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{21835}{96074} &:= \frac{(2 + (1^{83})) \times 5}{9 + (60 - (7 - 4))} := \frac{2 \times (1 \times (8 - (3 - 5)))}{(9 + (6 - (0 - 7))) \times 4} := \frac{(2 + (18 - 3)) \times 5}{(9 \times (6 \times (07))) - 4} := \frac{(2 + (1 + (8 \times 3))) \times 5}{9 \times (6 \times ((07 + 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (183 - 5)}{9 \times (60 + (7 \times 4))} := \frac{2 \times (1 \times (8 \times (3 \times 5)))}{96 \times ((07 + 4))} := \frac{2 \times (1 \times (8 \times 35))}{(9 + 607) \times 4} := \frac{(2 - (1^{83})) \times 5}{96 + (0 - 74)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{23897}{41560} &:= \frac{2 - (3 - (8 + (9 + 7)))}{4 + ((1 + 5) \times (6 - 0))} := \frac{2 + ((3 \times (8 + 9)) - 7)}{(4 \times (1 \times 5)) + 60} := \frac{2 + (3 + (8^{9-7}))}{4 \times (1 \times (5 \times (6 - 0)))} := \frac{(2 \times 38) + (9 + 7)}{4 + (156 - 0)} \\ &:= \frac{23 \times (8 - (9 - 7))}{4 \times ((1^5) \times 60)} := \frac{((2^3) \times 8) + 97}{(4 + 1) \times (56 - 0)} := \frac{2 \times ((3 + 89) \times 7)}{4 \times (1 \times 560)} := \frac{2 + ((3 \times 89) + 7)}{(4 - (1 - 5)) \times 60} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{26901}{34587} &:= \frac{(2 \times 6) - (9 \times (0 - 1))}{3 \times (4 + (5 \times (8 - 7)))} := \frac{2 \times (6 + (9 + (0 - 1)))}{((3 + 4) \times 5) + (8 - 7)} := \frac{26 - (9 \times (0 - 1))}{3 - (45 - 87)} := \frac{2 - (6 \times (9 \times (0 - 1)))}{3 \times (4 \times (5 + (8 - 7)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (6 + (90 \times 1))}{34 + (5 + 87)} := \frac{2 \times (69 - (0 - 1))}{3 \times (45 + (8 + 7))} := \frac{(2 \times 690) - 1}{3 \times (4 + 587)} := \frac{2 + (69 + (0 - 1))}{3 - (4 - ((5 + 8) \times 7))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{27168}{59430} &:= \frac{2^{7-1+6-8}}{(5 \times (9 + 4)) - 30} := \frac{(2 + (7 + (1^6))) \times 8}{5 \times (9 - (4 - 30))} := \frac{2 \times ((7 - (1^6)) \times 8)}{(5 \times (9 \times 4)) + 30} := \frac{2 - (71 \times (6 - 8))}{5 \times (9 \times (4 + (3 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times ((7 \times 16) - 8)}{5 \times (94 - (3 - 0))} := \frac{2 \times ((7 + 1) \times (6 \times 8))}{(5 + 9) \times (4 \times 30)} := \frac{2 \times (7 \times (1 \times (6 \times 8)))}{((5 \times 9) + 4) \times 30} := \frac{((2 \times (7 - 1)) - 6) \times 8}{5 \times (9 + (4 \times (3 - 0)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31408}{56927} &:= \frac{3 + (1 + (4 - (0 - 8)))}{5 + (6 - (9 - 27))} := \frac{(3 - (1 - (4 - 0))) \times 8}{5 - (6 - ((9^2) + 7))} := \frac{(3 \times (1 \times 40)) - 8}{(5 \times (6 \times (9 - 2))) - 7} := \frac{3 \times (1 \times (40 + 8))}{(5 \times (6 \times 9)) - (2 + 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + 1) \times (40 + 8)}{(5 \times (69 + 2)) - 7} := \frac{(3 - 1) \times (40 \times 8)}{5 \times (((6 + 9)^2) + 7)} := \frac{(3 - (1 - 40)) \times 8}{(56 \times (9 + 2)) - 7} := \frac{(3 + (1^4 + 0)) \times 8}{(5 \times (6 + (9 - 2))) - 7} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{35784}{69012} &:= \frac{(3 \times (5 - (7 - 8))) - 4}{6 + (9 - (0 - 12))} := \frac{3 - (5 \times (7 - (8 + 4)))}{6 \times (9 - (0 \times 12))} := \frac{(3 \times (5 + (7 + 8))) - 4}{6 \times (9 \times ((01 \times 2)))} := \frac{(3 + (5 - 7)) \times 84}{6 \times (9 \times ((01 + 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{3 + ((5 \times 7) + (8 - 4))}{69 - (0 - 12)} := \frac{(35 - 7) \times (8 + 4)}{6 \times (9 \times (012))} := \frac{(35 + (7 \times 8)) \times 4}{690 + 12} := \frac{3 \times (5 \times (7 \times (8 \times 4)))}{6 \times (90 \times 12)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{36045}{71289} &:= \frac{3 \times (6 - (0 - (4 + 5)))}{((7 + (1 + 2)) \times 8) + 9} := \frac{3 \times (60 \times (4 + 5))}{((7 - 1)^2) \times 89} := \frac{(3 + (6 - 0)) \times (4 \times 5)}{(7 - (1 + 2)) \times 89} := \frac{(3^6 + 0) - (4 + 5)}{(7 + 1) \times (2 \times 89)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times 60) + 45}{(7 - (1 \times 2)) \times 89} := \frac{3 \times (60 + 45)}{7 \times ((1^2) \times 89)} := \frac{3 \times (6 \times ((04 \times 5)))}{(7 + (1^2)) \times 89} := \frac{(3 + (6 - 0)) \times 45}{(7 + (1 \times 2)) \times 89} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{36045}{89712} &:= \frac{3 \times (6 - (0 - (4 + 5)))}{8 \times (9 - (7 - 12))} := \frac{3 \times (6 \times ((0 \times 4) + 5))}{8 \times (9 + (7 + 12))} := \frac{(3 + (6 - 0)) \times (4 \times 5)}{8 \times ((9 \times (7 - 1)) + 2)} := \frac{(3^6 + 0) - (4 + 5)}{(897 - 1) \times 2} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times 60) + 45}{8 \times ((9 \times (7 + 1)) - 2)} := \frac{3 \times (60 + 45)}{8 \times (97 + (1^2))} := \frac{3 \times (6 \times ((04 \times 5)))}{897 - (1^2)} := \frac{(3 + (6 - 0)) \times 45}{8 \times (9 \times (7 \times (1 \times 2)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{36974}{58102} &:= \frac{3 + (6 + (9 - (7 + 4)))}{5 + (8 + (1 \times (0 - 2)))} := \frac{3 + (6 + (9 + (7 - 4)))}{5 + (8 + (10 \times 2))} := \frac{3 \times (6 + ((9 - 7) \times 4))}{58 + (10 - 2)} := \frac{3 - (6 - ((9 \times 7) - 4))}{(5 \times (8 + 10)) - 2} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 + 6) \times 9) + (7 - 4)}{((5 + 8) \times 10) + 2} := \frac{3 + ((6^{9-7}) - 4)}{5 \times (8 + (1 - (0 - 2)))} := \frac{36 + (9 \times (7 - 4))}{5 - (8 - 102)} := \frac{3 + ((6 - (9 - 7))^4)}{(5 \times (81 - 0)) + 2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41769}{80325} &:= \frac{4 - (1 - (7 - (6 - 9)))}{(8 \times (0 \times 3)) + 25} := \frac{4 + (1 - (7 \times (6 - 9)))}{(8 + (0 - 3)) \times (2 \times 5)} := \frac{(4 - 17) \times (6 - 9)}{80 - ((3 - 2) \times 5)} := \frac{4 - (1 + (7 - 69))}{(8 + (0 - 3)) \times 25} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 + 1) \times 7) + 69}{(8 - (0 - 32)) \times 5} := \frac{((41 - 7) \times 6) - 9}{(80 - (3 + 2)) \times 5} := \frac{4 + ((1 + (7 + 6)) \times 9)}{(80 \times 3) + (2 \times 5)} := \frac{4 \times (1 + ((7 \times 6) + 9))}{80 \times ((3 - 2) \times 5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{42180}{65379} &:= \frac{4 + (2 \times (1 \times (8 - 0)))}{6 + (5 \times (3 - (7 - 9)))} := \frac{42 + (18 - 0)}{6 + (5 + (3 + 79))} := \frac{((4^2) - 1) \times (8 - 0)}{6 - (5 \times ((3 - 7) \times 9))} := \frac{4 \times (2 \times (1 \times 80))}{(65 - 3) \times (7 + 9)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (2 \times 1)) \times 80}{6 + (5 + (3 \times 79))} := \frac{((4 \times 2) + 1) \times 80}{(6 + ((5^3) - 7)) \times 9} := \frac{(4 - (2 - 1)) \times 80}{6 \times ((5^3) - (7 \times 9))} := \frac{(4 - 2) \times 180}{(6 + ((5 + 3) \times 7)) \times 9} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{43809}{72156} &:= \frac{(4 - 3) \times (8 - (0 - 9))}{7 \times (2 \times (1 - (5 - 6)))} := \frac{4 + (38 - (0 - 9))}{7 \times (2 - (1 - (5 + 6)))} := \frac{(4^3) + (80 + 9)}{7 \times ((2 \times 15) + 6)} := \frac{(4 + 3) \times (8 - (0 - 9))}{(7 \times 2) \times (1 - (5 - 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (3 \times (8 - (0 - 9)))}{7 \times ((2 + (1 + 5)) \times 6)} := \frac{4 + (3 + 809)}{7 \times ((2 \times (1 \times 5)) \times 6)} := \frac{(4^3) - (8 \times (0 - 9))}{7 \times (2 + (1 \times (5 \times 6)))} := \frac{(4 - 38) \times (0 - 9)}{7 \times (2 \times ((1 + 5) \times 6))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{45230}{76891} &:= \frac{4 + (5 - (2 - (3 - 0)))}{7 - (6 - (8 + (9 - 1)))} := \frac{45 + (2 + (3 - 0))}{7 + (6 + (8 \times (9 \times 1)))} := \frac{(4 \times (5^2)) - 30}{7 + ((6 + 8) \times (9 - 1))} := \frac{(4 \times (5^2)) + 30}{(7 + 6) \times (8 + (9 \times 1))} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (5 \times (2^3 + 0))}{(7 \times ((6 \times 8) - 9)) - 1} := \frac{(45 \times 2) - 30}{7 + (6 + (89 \times 1))} := \frac{4 \times ((5 - 2) \times 30)}{(76 - 8) \times (9 \times 1)} := \frac{(4 + (5 \times 2)) \times 30}{7 \times (6 \times (8 + (9 \times 1)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{45318}{69720} &:= \frac{4 + (5 + (3 + (1^8)))}{6 + (9 + (7 - (2 - 0)))} := \frac{4 - (5 - (3 \times (1 + 8)))}{(6 \times 9) - (7 \times (2 - 0))} := \frac{4 + (53 - 18)}{69 - (7 + (2 - 0))} := \frac{(4 \times (5 \times (3 \times 1))) - 8}{(6 - (9 - 7)) \times 20} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (5 + (3 + 18))}{(6 + (9 - 7)) \times 20} := \frac{4 + ((5^3) + (1^8))}{6 + (97 \times (2 - 0))} := \frac{4 - (5 - (31 \times 8))}{(6 \times (9 \times 7)) + (2 - 0)} := \frac{4 \times ((5^3 \times 1) - 8)}{(6^{9-7}) \times 20}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{45360}{91728} &:= \frac{4 \times (5 \times (3 \times 60))}{91 \times (72 + 8)} := \frac{4 + ((5^3) + (6 - 0))}{9 + (1 + (7 + (2^8)))} := \frac{(4 + 5) \times 360}{9 \times (1 \times 728)} := \frac{4 + (5 + (36 - 0))}{(9 \times (1 \times 7)) + 28} \\ &:= \frac{(45 + 3) \times 60}{91 \times (72 - 8)} := \frac{45 \times 360}{((9 - 1)^{7-2}) - 8} := \frac{4 \times (5 \times (3 \times (6 - 0)))}{(9 + 17) \times 28} := \frac{45 \times (3 + (6 - 0))}{91 + 728} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{46230}{78591} &:= \frac{4 \times (6 + (2 - (3 - 0)))}{7 + ((8 - 5) \times (9 \times 1))} := \frac{4 - (6 - (2 + 30))}{(7 \times 8) + (5 - (9 + 1))} := \frac{(4 + 6) \times (2 + (3 - 0))}{7 - (8 + (5 - 91))} := \frac{4 \times ((6 \times 2) + (3 - 0))}{7 + (85 + (9 + 1))} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (6 + (2 \times 30))}{7 + (8 \times (5 + (9 \times 1)))} := \frac{(4 + 6) \times (2^3 + 0)}{78 + (59 - 1)} := \frac{4 + (6 + 230)}{((7 \times 8) - 5) \times (9 - 1)} := \frac{((4 + 6)^2) \times (3 - 0)}{((7 \times 8) - 5) \times (9 + 1)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{48312}{57096} &:= \frac{4 - (8 - (3 + 12))}{5 - (7 + (0 - (9 + 6)))} := \frac{(4 \times (8 - (3 \times 1))) + 2}{5 - (7 \times (0 - (9 - 6)))} := \frac{4 \times (8 + (3 \times (1^2)))}{5 - (7 + (0 - (9 \times 6)))} := \frac{4 + ((8^{3-1}) \times 2)}{((5 \times (7 - 0)) - 9) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (83 \times (1 + 2))}{(5 \times (70 - 9)) - 6} := \frac{4 + ((8^{3-1}) - 2)}{5 + (70 + (9 - 6))} := \frac{483 + 12}{570 + (9 + 6)} := \frac{4 + ((8^3) + 12)}{570 + (9 \times 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{48312}{79056} &:= \frac{4 - (8 - (3 + 12))}{(7 - (9 + (0 - 5))) \times 6} := \frac{48 - (3 + 12)}{7 - (9 + (0 - 56))} := \frac{4 \times (8 + (3 \times (1^2)))}{7 + (9 - (0 - 56))} := \frac{48 + (31 - 2)}{(7 + (9 + 05)) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{4 - (8 - 312)}{(79 - (0 - 5)) \times 6} := \frac{((4 + 8) \times 31) + 2}{(7 + (90 + 5)) \times 6} := \frac{4 + ((8^{3-1}) - 2)}{7 + (90 + (5 + 6))} := \frac{4 + ((8^3) + (1^2))}{790 + 56} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{48503}{76219} &:= \frac{4 + (8 - (5 - (0 \times 3)))}{7 + (6 - (2 \times (1^9)))} := \frac{4 + (8 + (5 + (0 - 3)))}{7 - (6 - (2 + 19))} := \frac{(4 + (8 - (5 - 0))) \times 3}{7 + (6 + (2 \times (1 + 9)))} := \frac{4 - (8 - (50 + 3))}{7 + (62 - (1 - 9))} \\ &:= \frac{48 - (5 \times (0 - 3))}{(7 + (6 - (2 \times 1))) \times 9} := \frac{4 \times (8 + (5^{03}))}{76 \times (2 + (1 \times 9))} := \frac{(48 + 50) \times 3}{7 \times (6 \times (2 + (1 \times 9)))} := \frac{48 + (5 - (0 - 3))}{7 + ((6 + (2 + 1)) \times 9)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{49651}{78023} &:= \frac{4 + (9 + (6 - (5 \times 1)))}{7 - (8 + (0 - 23))} := \frac{((4 - 9) \times 6) + 51}{((7 + (8 - 0)) \times 2) + 3} := \frac{(4 \times (9 \times (6 - 5))) - 1}{7 - (8 \times (0 - (2 \times 3)))} := \frac{4 + (9 + (6 \times (5 + 1)))}{7 \times (8 - ((0 \times 2) - 3))} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times ((9 - 6) \times 5) - 1}{7 + (80 - (2 - 3))} := \frac{4 + (9 + (6 + 51))}{7 + (80 + 23)} := \frac{4 \times ((9 \times (6 + 5)) - 1)}{7 \times (80 + (2^3))} := \frac{(4 + (9 - 6)) \times 51}{(7 \times 80) - (2 - 3)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51394}{80762} &:= \frac{5 - (1 \times (3 - (9 - 4)))}{8 - (0 - (7 - (6 - 2)))} := \frac{5 - (1 + ((3 - 9) \times 4))}{(8 \times (07)) - (6 \times 2)} := \frac{5 + (1 + (39 + 4))}{8 - (0 - (7 + 62))} := \frac{(5 \times (1 \times (3 + 9))) - 4}{8 \times ((07 + (6 - 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{5 - ((1^3) - 94)}{80 + (76 - 2)} := \frac{((5 \times 13) - 9) \times 4}{8 \times (((07 \times 6) + 2))} := \frac{5 \times (1 + (3 + 94))}{8 - (0 - 762)} := \frac{5 \times ((1 + (3 \times 9)) \times 4)}{80 \times (7 + (6 - 2))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{51876}{94320} &:= \frac{5 + (18 - (7 - 6))}{(9 - (4 + 3)) \times 20} := \frac{5 + (1 \times (8 + (7 \times 6)))}{(9 + (4 - 3))^2 + 0} := \frac{5 - (1 - (8 + 76))}{(9 - (4 - 3)) \times 20} := \frac{5 + (1 + (87 + 6))}{9 \times (4 \times (3 + (2 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times (1 + (8 + (7 + 6)))}{(9 + (4 - 3)) \times 20} := \frac{5 - (1 - (8 - (7 - 6)))}{(9 + (4 - 3)) \times (2 - 0)} := \frac{(5 \times (1 \times 87)) - 6}{(9 + 4) \times (3 \times 20)} := \frac{5 - (1 - 876)}{(9 - 4) \times 320} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{53217}{94608} &:= \frac{5 \times (3^2 \times 1^7)}{94 - (6 - (0 - 8))} := \frac{5 + (32 + 17)}{94 - (6 + (0 - 8))} := \frac{53 + (21 + 7)}{9 \times ((4 \times (6 - 0)) - 8)} := \frac{(5^3) - (2 - (1 - 7))}{(9 \times (4 \times (6 - 0))) - 8} \\ &:= \frac{(5^3) + (2 - (1^7))}{(9 \times (4 \times (6 - 0))) + 8} := \frac{5 \times (3^{2+1^7})}{(9 - 4) \times (6 \times (08))} := \frac{(5 \times (32 \times 1)) - 7}{(94 - 60) \times 8} := \frac{(5 \times (32 - 1)) + 7}{9 \times ((4 \times (6 - 0)) + 8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{59130}{86724} &:= \frac{5 + (9 + (1^3 + 0))}{8 - (6 - ((7 - 2) \times 4))} := \frac{5 \times (9 - (1 \times (3 - 0)))}{8 - (6 - (7 \times (2 + 4)))} := \frac{5 + (9 + (1 + 30))}{8 + (((6 \times (7 + 2)) + 4)} := \frac{5 \times (9 + (1 \times (3 - 0)))}{8 \times (6 + (7 + (2 - 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 \times (9 \times 1)) + 30}{8 - (6 \times (7 - 24))} := \frac{5 \times ((9 - 1) \times (3 - 0))}{8 \times (((6 + 7) \times 2) - 4)} := \frac{5 \times (9 \times (1 \times (3 - 0)))}{8 - (6 - ((7^2) \times 4))} := \frac{5 \times ((9 - 1) \times 30)}{(8 + (6 \times 72)) \times 4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{61740}{89523} &:= \frac{(6 + (1 \times 7)) \times 40}{(8 \times 95) - (2 \times 3)} := \frac{6 + (1 - (7 - 40))}{8 + ((9 \times 5) + (2 + 3))} := \frac{6 + (1 \times (74 - 0))}{89 + ((5 - 2)^3)} := \frac{(6 - (1^7)) \times (4 - 0)}{8 - (9 - (5 \times (2 \times 3)))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - 1) \times (7 \times (4 - 0))}{((8 + 95) \times 2) - 3} := \frac{6 + (174 - 0)}{(((8 + 9) \times 5) + 2) \times 3} := \frac{(6 - 1) \times (7 \times 40)}{8 + (((9 \times 5)^2) - 3)} := \frac{(6 - (1 - 7)) \times 40}{8 \times ((9 \times (5 \times 2)) - 3)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{62307}{94815} &:= \frac{(6 \times (2 + (3 - 0))) - 7}{9 + ((4 \times 8) - (1 + 5))} := \frac{(6^2) + (3 - (0 - 7))}{(9 - (4 - (8 + 1))) \times 5} := \frac{(6 - 2) \times (30 - 7)}{((9 \times 4) - (8 \times 1)) \times 5} := \frac{((6^2) \times (3 - 0)) + 7}{(9 - 4) \times ((8 - 1) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (2 - (3 \times (0 - 7)))}{(9 + ((4 \times 8) + 1)) \times 5} := \frac{(6 + 2) \times (30 - 7)}{(9 + (48 - 1)) \times 5} := \frac{6 \times (2 \times (30 - 7))}{((9 \times 4) - 8) \times 15} := \frac{(6^2) \times (30 - 7)}{9 \times (4 \times ((8 - 1) \times 5))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{72135}{90684} &:= \frac{7 \times (2 + (1 - (3 - 5)))}{(9 + (0 - (6 - 8))) \times 4} := \frac{7 \times (2 + (1 \times (3 + 5)))}{90 - (6 - (8 - 4))} := \frac{(7^2 \times 1^3) \times 5}{(9 - (0 - 68)) \times 4} := \frac{7 \times (2 \times ((1 + 3) \times 5))}{(90 + (6 - 8)) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + (2 \times 1)) \times 35}{9 \times (((06 \times 8) - 4))} := \frac{(7 + 21) \times (3 \times 5)}{(90 \times 6) - (8 + 4)} := \frac{((7 \times 2) - 1) \times 35}{(90 \times 6) + (8 \times 4)} := \frac{7 \times (2 \times (1 \times 35))}{(9 \times (068)) + 4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{78246}{931507} &:= \frac{7 - 8 - 2 + 4 \times 6}{(9 - 3 - 1) \times 5 + 0} := \frac{7 \times (8 - 2 + 4 \times 6)}{(9 - 3 - 1) \times 50} := \frac{7 \times (8 + 2 - 4) \times 6}{(9 - 3 \times 1) \times 50} := \frac{7^{8-2-4} \times 6}{(9 - 3 + 1) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (8^2 - 4 + 6)}{(9 + (3 - 1)) \times 50} := \frac{7 \times (82 - 4 - 6)}{(9 + 3 \times 1) \times 50} := \frac{78 \times (2 \times 4 + 6)}{(9 \times 3 - 1) \times 50} := \frac{7 \times 8 \times (24 + 6)}{(9 + 31) \times 50} \end{aligned}$$

• Four Digit's Numerator

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{2871}{459360} &:= \frac{((2 \times 8) - (7 \times 1))}{(4 \times (5 \times (9 + (3 + 60))))} := \frac{((2 \times 8) + (7 + 1))}{((4 + (5 \times (9 + 3))) \times 60)} := \frac{(2 + (8 - (7 \times 1)))}{(4 \times ((5 \times (9 + 3)) + 60))} := \frac{(2 + (8 + (7 + 1)))}{((4 - (5 - 9)) \times 360)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (8 + 71))}{((45 - 9) \times 360)} := \frac{(2 + (87 + 1))}{(4 \times (5 \times ((9 + 3) \times 60)))} := \frac{(28 + (7 \times 1))}{((4 \times 5) + (93 \times 60))} := \frac{(287 + 1)}{((4^5) \times (9 + (36 - 0)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{3108}{257964} &:= \frac{(3 - (1^{08}))}{((2 \times (5 + 79)) - (6 - 4))} := \frac{(3 - (10 - 8))}{(2 + ((57 - (9 \times 6))^4))} := \frac{(3 \times (1 \times (0 + 8)))}{(((2^5) \times (7 \times 9)) - (6 \times 4))} := \frac{(3 \times (10 - 8))}{(2 \times (5 + ((7 + (9 \times 6)) \times 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (1^{08}))}{(((2^5) - 7) \times 9) + (6 \times 4)} := \frac{(3 + (1 - (0 - 8)))}{(25 + (7 + 964))} := \frac{(3 + (1^{08}))}{(2 - (5 \times (7 - (9 + 64))))} := \frac{(3 + (10 - 8))}{(((2^5) + 7) \times 9) + 64} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{3507}{164829} &:= \frac{((3 \times (5 - 0)) + 7)}{(1 + ((64 \times (8 \times 2)) + 9))} := \frac{((3 - 5) \times (0 - 7))}{((1 + 6) \times (4 + ((8 + 2) \times 9)))} := \frac{(3 - (5 \times (0 \times 7)))}{(1 \times (6 + (((4 + 8)^2) - 9)))} := \frac{(3 - (5 + (0 - 7)))}{(1 + (6 - (4 - (8 \times 29))))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (5 - (0 \times 7)))}{(1 + ((6 \times (4 \times (8 \times 2))) - 9))} := \frac{(3 + (5 - (0 - 7)))}{(1 + ((6 \times (4 \times 8)) + (2^9)))} := \frac{(3 + (5 + (0 - 7)))}{(1 \times (6 + (4 + (8 + 29))))} := \frac{(35 + (0 - 7))}{(1 + ((6^4) + (8 + (2 + 9))))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{3508}{217496} &:= \frac{((3 \times (5 - 0)) - 8)}{(2 \times ((1^7) + (4 \times (9 \times 6))))} := \frac{((3 + (5 - 0)) \times 8)}{((2 - (1 - 7)) \times 496)} := \frac{(3 - (5 \times (0 \times 8)))}{((2 - (1 \times (7 - (4 \times 9)))) \times 6)} := \frac{(3 - (5 + (0 - 8)))}{((2 \times (174 + 9)) + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (5 - (0 - 8)))}{(2 + (1 \times ((7^4) + (9 + 6))))} := \frac{(3 + (5 - (0 \times 8)))}{((2 - (1^7)) \times 496)} := \frac{(3 + (5 - (0 - 8)))}{(2 + ((174 - 9) \times 6))} := \frac{(35 + (0 - 8))}{((2 + (1 + (7 \times 4))) \times (9 \times 6))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{3648}{105792} &:= \frac{3 - (6 + (4 - 8))}{((1 + (0 - (5 - 7))) \times 9) + 2} := \frac{36 - (4 \times 8)}{1 \times (0 - ((5 - (7 \times 9)) \times 2))} := \frac{(3 \times (6 - 4)) + 8}{1 - (0 - (5 \times (79 + 2)))} := \frac{(3 \times (6 + 4)) - 8}{(1 - (0 - 57)) \times (9 + 2)} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (6 - 4)) \times 8}{(1 - (0 - 579)) \times 2} := \frac{3^{6+4-8}}{1 \times ((05 + ((7 + 9)^2)))} := \frac{3 \times (6 + 48)}{(1 - (0 - 57)) \times (9^2)} := \frac{(3 \times 64) - 8}{(1 - (0 - 57)) \times 92} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{3708}{415296} &:= \frac{(3 - (7 \times (0 \times 8)))}{(4 \times ((1 - (5 - (2 \times 9))) \times 6))} := \frac{(3 - (7 + (0 - 8)))}{((4 - (1 - 5)) \times (2 + (9 \times 6)))} := \frac{(3 \times (7 - (0 \times 8)))}{(4 \times ((1 + 5) \times (2 + 96)))} := \frac{(3 \times (7 \times (0 + 8)))}{((((4 + 1)^5) + (2 + 9)) \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (7 - (0 \times 8)))}{(4 \times (1 \times (5 \times (2 + (9 \times 6))))} := \frac{(3 + (7 - (0 - 8)))}{((4 + (15 + 2)) \times 96)} := \frac{(3 + (7 + (0 - 8)))}{(4 \times (1 + (52 + (9 - 6))))} := \frac{(37 - (0 \times 8))}{((4 - (1 - 5)) \times ((2^9) + 6))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{3798}{140526} &:= \frac{((3 \times (7 - 9)) + 8)}{(1 + (4 - (0 - (5 + (2^6))))))} := \frac{((3 + (7 - 9)) \times 8)}{(((140 + 5) \times 2) + 6)} := \frac{((3 + (7 - 9))^8)}{(1 - (4 \times (0 - (5 - (2 - 6))))))} := \frac{(3 \times (7 - (9 - 8)))}{(140 + 526)} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (7 + (9 + 8)))}{(1 + ((4^{05}) - 26))} := \frac{(3 + (7 + (9 - 8)))}{(1 + (((4 \times (0 + 5))^2) + 6))} := \frac{(3 + (79 - 8))}{((14^{05-2}) - 6)} := \frac{(37 + (9 - 8))}{((140 \times (5 \times 2)) + 6)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4358}{270196} &:= \frac{(((4 - 3)^5)^8)}{(2 + (7 + (0 - (1 - (9 \times 6))))))} := \frac{((4^3) - (5 - 8))}{(2 + ((701 - 9) \times 6))} := \frac{((4^3) + (5 - 8))}{(2 + (70 \times (1 \times (9 \times 6))))} := \frac{((4^3) - 58)}{((2 + (70 - (1 + 9))) \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - (3 + (5 - 8)))}{(2 \times (70 + (1 \times (9 \times 6))))} := \frac{(4 + ((3 \times 5) + 8))}{((270 + (1 \times 9)) \times 6)} := \frac{(4 + (3 \times (5 + 8)))}{((2 \times (70 \times 19)) + 6)} := \frac{(43 - (5 \times 8))}{(2 + (70 + (19 \times 6)))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{4518}{293670} &:= \frac{(((4 \times 5) + 1) \times 8)}{((29 - 3) \times (6 \times 70))} := \frac{((4 \times (5 \times 1)) + 8)}{((29 + (3 - 6)) \times 70)} := \frac{((4 \times 5) - (1^8))}{((2 + 93) \times (6 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{((4 \times 5) - (1 + 8))}{(2 - (9 - ((3^6) - (7 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - (5 - (1 \times 8)))}{((29 + 36) \times (7 - 0))} := \frac{(4 + (5 - (1 \times 8)))}{(2 - ((9 - (3 \times 6)) \times (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 + (5 \times (1^8)))}{((2^9) - (3 - (6 + 70)))} := \frac{(4 + (5 + (1 - 8)))}{(2 \times (((9 + 3) \times 6) - (7 - 0)))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5067}{238149} &:= \frac{((5 \times (0 \times 6)) + 7)}{(2 + ((3 \times (8 \times 14)) - 9))} := \frac{(5 - ((0 \times 6) - 7))}{(2 \times (3 \times (81 + (4 + 9))))} := \frac{(5 - (0 - (6 + 7)))}{((2 + (((3 \times 8) - 1) \times 4)) \times 9)} := \frac{(5 - (0 - (6 - 7)))}{(2 \times (3 + ((8 - 1) \times (4 + 9))))} \\ &:= \frac{(50 - (6 \times 7))}{(((2 + 3) \times (81 - 4)) - 9)} := \frac{(50 - (6 - 7))}{(2 + (3 + (((8 - 1)^4) - 9)))} := \frac{(50 + (6 + 7))}{((2 + (3 + (81 \times 4))) \times 9)} := \frac{(50 + (6 - 7))}{(((2 \times (3 \times 8)) - 1) \times 49)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5103}{287469} &:= \frac{(5 \times (1 \times (0 + 3)))}{((2 - (8 + 7)) \times (4 - 69))} := \frac{(5 + (1^{03}))}{((2^8) + ((7 \times 4) + (6 \times 9)))} := \frac{(5 + (1 + (0 - 3)))}{(2 + (8 + ((7 \times (4 \times 6)) - 9)))} := \frac{(5 + (10 + 3))}{(2 \times (((87 - 4) \times 6) + 9))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + (10 - 3))}{((2^8) + (7 \times (4 \times (6 + 9))))} := \frac{(51 - (0 \times 3))}{(2 + (87 \times ((4 \times 6) + 9)))} := \frac{(51 - (0 - 3))}{(((2 \times 8) + (7 \times 46)) \times 9)} := \frac{(510 + 3)}{(2 \times ((8 + (7^4)) \times 6) - 9)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5168}{273904} &:= \frac{(5 - (1 - (6 - 8)))}{(2 + (7 + (3 + (90 + 4))))} := \frac{(5 - (1 \times (6 - 8)))}{((2^7) + (3^{9-04}))} := \frac{(5 - (1 + (6 - 8)))}{(2 \times (73 + (90 - 4)))} := \frac{(5 + ((1^6) + 8))}{(((2 + 7)^3) + (9 - (0 - 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + (1 - (6 - 8)))}{(((2^7-3) + 90) \times 4)} := \frac{(5 + (1 \times (6 - 8)))}{((2 \times 73) + (9 - (0 - 4)))} := \frac{(5 + (1 + (6 + 8)))}{((2 - (7 - (3 \times 90))) \times 4)} := \frac{(5 + (1 + (6 - 8)))}{(((27 - 3) \times (9 - 0)) - 4)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5346}{197802} &:= \frac{(((5 + 3) \times 4) + 6)}{((1 + (9 \times (78 - 0))) \times 2)} := \frac{(((5 - 3) \times 4) - 6)}{(1 + ((9 \times 7) + (8 - (0 - 2))))} := \frac{(((5 - 3)^4) + 6)}{(19 - (7 - 802))} := \frac{(((5 \times (3 - 4)) + 6))}{(197 - (80 \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 - 3) \times (4 + 6)}{(1 - ((9 \times 7) - 802))} := \frac{(5 - (3 - (4 \times 6)))}{(((19 - 7) \times 80) + 2)} := \frac{(5 - (3 + (4 - 6)))}{(1 - (9 + (78 \times (0 - 2))))} := \frac{(53 - 46)}{(1 + (((9 - 7)^8 + 0) + 2))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5934}{172086} &:= \frac{(5 - (9 - (3 + 4)))}{((1^{72} + 0) + 86)} := \frac{(5 - (9 \times (3 - 4)))}{(((1 + (7^2 + 0)) \times 8) + 6)} := \frac{(5 \times (9 - (3 + 4)))}{(((17 + 20) \times 8) - 6)} := \frac{(5 \times (9 - (3 - 4)))}{(1 \times ((7 \times 208) - 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + ((9 + 3) \times 4))}{((1^7) + ((2^{08}) \times 6))} := \frac{(5 + (9 - (3 \times 4)))}{(1 + (7 + (2 - (0 - (8 \times 6)))))} := \frac{(5 + (9 - (3 + 4)))}{(1 + ((7 \times (20 + 8)) + 6))} := \frac{(5 + (93 - 4))}{((17 \times (20 \times 8)) + 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5943}{271680} &:= \frac{((5 \times 9) + 4) \times 3}{(2 \times (7 \times (1 \times (6 \times 80))))} := \frac{((5 \times (9 - 4)) + 3)}{(2 \times ((7 + (1^6)) \times 80))} := \frac{((5 + 9) \times (4 \times 3))}{(2 \times ((7 + 1) \times (6 \times 80)))} := \frac{(5 \times (9 + (4 \times 3)))}{((2 + (7 + 1)) \times (6 \times 80))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (9 - (4 \times 3)))}{(2 \times ((7 + (1 - 6)) \times 80))} := \frac{(5 + (9 \times 43))}{(2 \times (7 \times (16 \times 80)))} := \frac{(5 + (9 \times (4 - 3)))}{((2 + (7 - (1^6))) \times 80)} := \frac{(5 + (9 + (4 \times 3)))}{(2 \times ((7 - (1^6)) \times 80))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6051}{284397} &:= \frac{((6 \times (0 + 5)) + 1)}{(2 + ((8 + (4 + 3)) \times 97))} := \frac{(6 - ((0 \times 5) - 1))}{((2 \times (8 \times ((4 \times 3) + 9))) - 7)} := \frac{(6 - (0 - (5 - 1)))}{(((2 + (8 + 43)) \times 9) - 7)} := \frac{(6 - (0 \times 51))}{(2 - ((8 - (4 \times (3 + 9))) \times 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 + ((0 \times 5) - 1))}{((2^8) - ((4 \times 3) - 9) \times 7)} := \frac{(6 + (0 - (5 \times 1)))}{((2 \times (8 + (4^3))) - 97)} := \frac{(6 + (0 - (5 - 1)))}{(2 + ((8 \times 4) - (3 - (9 \times 7))))} := \frac{(60 - 51)}{(((2 + 8) \times (4 + 39)) - 7)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6279}{408135} &:= \frac{(((6 - 2) \times 7) - 9)}{((4 - (0 - (81 \times 3))) \times 5)} := \frac{((6 \times (2 + 7)) + 9)}{(4 - (0 - ((8 \times (1 + 3)) - 5)))} := \frac{((6 + (2 - 7))^9)}{((4 - (0 - (8 + (1^3)))) \times 5)} := \frac{(6 - (2 - (7 - 9)))}{(((4 - ((0 \times 8) - 1))^3) + 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 - (2 + (7 - 9)))}{(408 - (13 + 5))} := \frac{(6 \times (2 - (7 - 9)))}{(4 \times (0 + ((81 - 3) \times 5)))} := \frac{(6 + (2 - (7 - 9)))}{(408 - (1 - (3^5)))} := \frac{(6 + (27 \times 9))}{(((40 \times 81) - 3) \times 5)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6294}{173085} &:= \frac{(((6 \times 2) - 9) \times 4)}{(1 \times ((7^3 + 0) - (8 + 5)))} := \frac{((6 \times (2 + 9)) + 4)}{(((1 + 7) \times (30 \times 8)) + 5)} := \frac{((6 + (2 + 9)) \times 4)}{((1 + (7 \times (3 - 0))) \times 85)} := \frac{(6 - ((2 - 9) \times 4))}{(((1 + (7 + (3 - 0))) \times 85)} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 + ((2 \times 9) + 4))}{(1 \times (7 \times ((30 - 8) \times 5)))} := \frac{(6 + ((2 \times 9) - 4))}{((17 \times 30) + (8 \times 5))} := \frac{(6 + (2 \times (9 + 4)))}{((1 + (7 \times (3 - 0))) \times (8 \times 5))} := \frac{(6 + (2 \times (9 - 4)))}{(((1 + (7 + (3 - 0))) \times (8 \times 5))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6372}{195408} &:= \frac{((6 \times 3) - (7 + 2))}{(1 - ((9 \times 5) - (40 \times 8)))} := \frac{((6 - 3) \times (7 \times 2))}{((1 + ((9 - 5) \times 40)) \times 8)} := \frac{((6 - 3) \times (7 - 2))}{((1 + 9) \times (54 + (0 - 8)))} := \frac{(6 - (3 - (7 + 2)))}{(((1 - (9 - (54 - 0))) \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (3 + (7 + 2)))}{((1 + (9 \times 5)) \times (40 + 8))} := \frac{(6 \times (3 + (7 - 2)))}{((1 + (9 \times 5)) \times (4 \times (0 + 8)))} := \frac{(6 + (3 \times (7 - 2)))}{(19 + (5^4 - 0 \times 8))} := \frac{(6 + (3 + (7 + 2)))}{(1 \times (((9 + 5) \times 40) - 8))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6534}{120879} &:= \frac{6 - (5 + (3 - 4))}{1 + (20 - (8 \times (7 - 9)))} := \frac{6 + (5 - (3 + 4))}{1 + (2 + (0 - (8 - 79)))} := \frac{6 - (5 - (3 + 4))}{1 \times (20 + (8 \times (7 + 9)))} := \frac{6 + (5 + (3 - 4))}{120 + ((8 \times 7) + 9)} \\
 &:= \frac{6 + (5 + (3 + 4))}{(1 - (20 - (8 \times 7))) \times 9} := \frac{6 + ((5 - 3) \times 4)}{1 + ((2^8) - (7 - 9))} := \frac{65 + (3^4)}{1 + (20 \times ((8 + 7) \times 9))} := \frac{(6 \times (5 + 3)) + 4}{(120 \times 8) - (7 - 9)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6702}{395418} &:= \frac{((6 - 7) \times (0 - 2))}{((3 \times ((9 + 5) \times (4 - 1))) - 8)} := \frac{(6 - (7 \times (0 \times 2)))}{(3 - (9 - (5 \times (4 \times 18))))} := \frac{(6 - (7 + (0 - 2)))}{(3 - (9 - (5 \times (4 + (1 + 8))))} := \frac{(6 \times (7 - (0 \times 2)))}{((3 - 9) \times (5 - 418))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 + (7 - (0 \times 2)))}{((3 \times ((9 - 5)^4)) - (1^8))} := \frac{(6 + (7 - (0 - 2)))}{(3 + (((9 \times 5) + 4) \times 18))} := \frac{(6 + (7 + (0 - 2)))}{(((3 + 9) \times 54) + (1^8))} := \frac{(67 - (0 \times 2))}{(3954 - (1^8))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6708}{194532} &:= \frac{((6 \times (7 - 0)) + 8)}{(1 + (9 + (45 \times 32)))} := \frac{((6 - 7) \times (0 - 8))}{(((1 + 9) \times ((4 \times 5) + 3)) + 2)} := \frac{(6 - (7 \times (0 \times 8)))}{(1 + (9 + (4 + (5 \times 32))))} := \frac{(6 - (7 + (0 - 8)))}{((19 \times (4 + 5)) + 32)} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (7 - (0 \times 8)))}{(1 + ((9 \times (45 \times 3)) + 2))} := \frac{(6 + (7 - (0 \times 8)))}{(1 + ((9 \times (45 - 3)) - 2))} := \frac{(6 + (7 + (0 - 8)))}{(1 - (9 \times (4 \times (5 - (3^2))))} := \frac{(6 + (70 + 8))}{(((1 + (9 \times 45)) \times (3 \times 2))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6709}{234815} &:= \frac{((6 + (7 - 0)) \times 9)}{((2 + 3) \times (4 + 815))} := \frac{((6 - 7) \times (0 - 9))}{((2 + (3 + 4)) \times ((8 - 1) \times 5))} := \frac{(6 - (7 \times (0 \times 9)))}{(2 \times ((3 - (4 - 8)) \times 15))} := \frac{(6 - (7 + (0 - 9)))}{(2 \times ((3 \times 48) + (1 - 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (7 - (0 \times 9)))}{(2 \times (3 \times ((48 + 1) \times 5)))} := \frac{(6 + (7 - (0 \times 9)))}{((2 + ((3^4) + (8 \times 1))) \times 5)} := \frac{(6 + (7 - (0 - 9)))}{(2 + (3 \times (4^{8+1-5})))} := \frac{(6 + (7 + (0 - 9)))}{(2 \times ((3 + (4 + (8 - 1))) \times 5))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6834}{105927} &:= \frac{6 + (8 - (3 \times 4))}{1 \times (0 - (5 - (9 + 27)))} := \frac{(6 - (8 - 3)) \times 4}{1 \times (((05 \times (9 + 2)) + 7))} := \frac{6 - (8 - 34)}{1 - (0 - (5 \times (92 + 7)))} := \frac{6^{8-3-4}}{1 \times ((05 + ((9^2) + 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times (8 + (3 - 4))}{((10^5) + 92) \times 7} := \frac{(6 \times 8) + (3 \times 4)}{10 \times (5 + ((9^2) + 7))} := \frac{(6 + (8 + 3)) \times 4}{1059 + (2 - 7)} := \frac{68 + (3 \times 4)}{10 \times (5 - (9 - (2^7)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7083}{269154} &:= \frac{((7 \times (0 \times 8)) + 3)}{(2 \times (6 - (9 - (15 \times 4))))} := \frac{(7 - ((0 \times 8) - 3))}{(2 + (6 \times (9 + (1 \times 54))))} := \frac{(7 - (0 - (8 + 3)))}{(2 + (691 - (5 + 4)))} := \frac{(7 - (0 - (8 - 3)))}{(((2 \times (6 \times 9)) + (1 + 5)) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 - (0 \times 83))}{(2 - (6 \times (9 + (1 - 54))))} := \frac{(7 + ((0 \times 8) - 3))}{((2 - (6 \times (9 - 15))) \times 4)} := \frac{(7 + (0 - (8 - 3)))}{(2 \times (6 + ((9 - (1^5)) \times 4)))} := \frac{(70 + (8 + 3))}{((2 + ((6 \times 9) + 1)) \times 54)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8064}{175392} &:= \frac{((8 \times (0+6)) + 4)}{(1 + (7 + (((5^3) \times 9) - 2)))} := \frac{((8 \times (0+6)) - 4)}{(1 + ((7 \times (5^3)) + (9^2)))} := \frac{(8 - (0 \times 64))}{(1 \times ((75 + (3+9)) \times 2))} := \frac{(8 \times (0 + (6+4)))}{(1 + (((7+5)^3) + (9+2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 \times (0 + (6-4)))}{(1 \times ((7+5) \times ((3 \times 9) + 2)))} := \frac{(8^{06-4})}{(17 + ((5^3) \times (9+2)))} := \frac{(8 + ((0 \times 6) - 4))}{(1 + (7 - (5 - (3 + (9^2)))))} := \frac{(80 + (6 \times 4))}{(1 \times (75 + (3^{9-2})))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8132}{467590} &:= \frac{((8 - (1-3))^2)}{(46 \times ((7 \times 5) + 90))} := \frac{((8 + (1+3))^2)}{(46 \times ((7-5) \times 90))} := \frac{((8 + (1-3))^2)}{((4 + (6 \times 7)) \times (5 \times (9-0)))} := \frac{(8 - (1 - (3^2)))}{((4+6) \times (7 - (5-90)))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 - (1 + (3+2)))}{(((4 - (6-7)) \times 5) + 90)} := \frac{(8 \times (1 \times (3^2)))}{(4 + (6 + (7 \times 590)))} := \frac{(8 + (1 + (3+2)))}{(46 + (759 - 0))} := \frac{(81 - (3+2))}{((4 + (6 \times 7)) \times (5 + 90))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8310}{427965} &:= \frac{((8 \times 3) - 10)}{(((42 + 79) \times 6) - 5)} := \frac{((8-3) \times 10)}{(((4 \times (2^7)) + (9-6)) \times 5)} := \frac{(8 - (3 - (1-0)))}{(((4 + 27) \times 9) + (6 \times 5))} := \frac{(8 - (3 + (1-0)))}{(4 + (2 \times (((7+9) \times 6) + 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 \times (3 - (1-0)))}{(4 + (((2 \times 79) + 6) \times 5))} := \frac{(8 \times (3 \times (1-0)))}{(4 \times (279 + (6 \times 5)))} := \frac{(8 \times (3 + 10))}{(4 \times ((2 \times (7 \times 96)) - 5))} := \frac{(8 + (3 - (1-0)))}{(((4 + (2 + 79)) \times 6) + 5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8365}{217490} &:= \frac{(((8 \times 3) - 6) \times 5)}{(2 \times ((17-4) \times 90))} := \frac{((8 \times 3) + 65)}{(2 + (1 + ((7^4) - 90)))} := \frac{(8 - (3 \times (6-5)))}{(2 \times (1 \times (74 - (9-0))))} := \frac{(8 - (3 + (6-5)))}{(2 + (1 + (7 + (4+90))))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 \times ((3 \times 6) + 5))}{(2 \times (1 \times ((7^4) - (9-0))))} := \frac{(8^{3-6+5})}{((2^{1 \times 7}) \times (4 + (9-0)))} := \frac{(8 + (3 + (6-5)))}{(((2+1) \times 74) + 90)} := \frac{(8 + (36-5))}{(2 \times (17 + 490))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8623}{457019} &:= \frac{((8 \times 6) - (2+3))}{(((4 \times 570) - (1^9))} := \frac{(8 - (6 - (2^3)))}{(((4-57) \times (0 - (1+9)))} := \frac{(8 - (6 - (2-3)))}{(4 + ((5 \times (7 - (0-1))) + 9))} := \frac{(8 - (6 + (2-3)))}{(((4 \times (5 \times (7-0))) + 19)} \\ &:= \frac{(8^{6-2-3})}{(((4 - (57-0)) \times (1-9))} := \frac{(8 + (6 - (2+3)))}{(((4-57) \times (0 - (1 \times 9)))} := \frac{(8 + (6 \times (2-3)))}{(45 + (70 - (1 \times 9)))} := \frac{(8 + (6 + (2+3)))}{(((4-57) \times (0-19))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8730}{196425} &:= \frac{((8 \times 7) + 30)}{(((1 + 964) \times 2) + 5)} := \frac{((8 \times 7) - 30)}{((1 + (((9 \times 6) + 4) \times 2)) \times 5)} := \frac{(8 - (7 - (3-0)))}{((1 + (9 + (6 + (4-2)))) \times 5)} := \frac{(8 \times (7 - (3-0)))}{(((1 + (9 + (6-4)))^2) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(8 \times (7 + (3-0)))}{((1+9) \times ((6^4-2) \times 5))} := \frac{(8 + (7 - (3-0)))}{((1 - (9 - (64-2))) \times 5)} := \frac{(8 + (7 + (3-0)))}{(((1 + (9 + (6+4)))^2) + 5)} := \frac{(87 + (3-0))}{(1 \times ((9^6-4) \times 25))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9518}{204637} &:= \frac{((9 - (5-1)) \times 8)}{(20 \times ((4 \times (6+3)) + 7))} := \frac{((9 \times (5+1)) + 8)}{((20 \times (4+63)) - 7)} := \frac{((9 \times (5-1)) - 8)}{(2 \times (0 + ((46-3) \times 7)))} := \frac{(9 - (5 - (1 \times 8)))}{((2 - (0-4)) \times (6+37))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 - (5 \times (1^8)))}{(2 - (0 - (4 \times ((6-3) \times 7))))} := \frac{(9 + (5 - (1 \times 8)))}{((2 \times (0 + 46)) + 37)} := \frac{(9 + (5 + 18))}{((2^{04}) \times (6+37))} := \frac{(95 - (1-8))}{(2 - (0 - (4 + ((6-3)^7))))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9784}{210356} &:= \frac{((9 + (7+8)) \times 4)}{((2 \times 1035) - 6)} := \frac{((9 + (7-8)) \times 4)}{(2 \times ((10 \times 35) - 6))} := \frac{((9-7) \times (8-4))}{(2 \times ((10 \times (3+5)) + 6))} := \frac{(9 - (7 - (8 \times 4)))}{(2 + ((1 + (0 - (3-5)))^6))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 - (7 - (8-4)))}{((2 \times (10-3)) - (5-6))} := \frac{(9 + (7 - (8+4)))}{(2 - ((1 + (0 - (3 \times 5))) \times 6))} := \frac{(9 + (7 - (8-4)))}{(21 - (0 - ((3^5) - 6)))} := \frac{(9 + (7 + (8 \times 4)))}{(2 + (((1 - (0-3))^5) + 6))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9864}{350172} &:= \frac{(((9-8)^6) \times 4)}{((3 \times (50-1)) - (7-2))} := \frac{((9 - (8-6)) \times 4)}{((3 + (501-7)) \times 2)} := \frac{((9 \times 8) - (6-4))}{(35 \times (0 - (1-72)))} := \frac{((9 \times 8) - 64)}{(((3-50) \times (1-7)) + 2)} \\ &:= \frac{((9-8) \times (6+4))}{(3 + ((50 \times (1 \times 7)) + 2))} := \frac{((9-8) \times (6-4))}{(3 - (5 + (0 - (1+72))))} := \frac{(9 \times ((8-6) \times 4))}{(3 \times ((50 \times 17) + 2))} := \frac{(98 + (6-4))}{(3501 + (7^2))} \end{aligned}$$

3.8 9 Equivalent Blocks

• Five Digit's Numerator

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{12705}{86394} &:= \frac{1 + (2 + (7 - (0 \times 5)))}{8 - (6 \times (3 - (9 + 4)))} := \frac{1 + (2 + (7 - (0 - 5)))}{86 + (3 + (9 + 4))} := \frac{1 + ((2 \times (7 - 0)) + 5)}{((8 + 6) \times 3) + 94} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (2 \times (7 - (0 - 5)))}{8 + (6 + (39 \times 4))} := \frac{(1 - (2 - (7 - 0))) \times 5}{((8 + 6) \times 3) + 9} \times 4 := \frac{(1^2) \times (7 \times (05))}{8 + ((6 \times 39) - 4)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (2 \times 7)) \times (0 - 5)}{(8 \times 6) + 394} := \frac{1 \times (2 \times (7 \times (05)))}{(8^{6-3}) - (9 \times 4)} := \frac{(1 + (2 \times 70)) \times 5}{((8 \times 6) + 3) \times 94} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{12859}{36740} &:= \frac{1 + (2 + (8 + (5 - 9)))}{3 + (6 + (7 + (4 - 0)))} := \frac{(1^2) + ((8 - 5) \times 9)}{(3 + (6 - 7)) \times 40} := \frac{1 + (2 - (8 \times (5 - 9)))}{((3 \times 6) + 7) \times (4 - 0)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (2 + (8 + (5 \times 9)))}{(3 - (6 - 7)) \times 40} := \frac{(1 + (2 \times (8 - 5))) \times 9}{(3 + (6 \times 7)) \times (4 - 0)} := \frac{1 \times (2 \times ((8 \times 5) + 9))}{(3 + 67) \times (4 - 0)} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + 28) \times 5) + 9}{((3 \times 6) - 7) \times 40} := \frac{1 \times (2 \times (8 \times (5 + 9)))}{(3 + (6 + 7)) \times 40} := \frac{(1 + 28) \times (5 + 9)}{(36 - 7) \times 40} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{12876}{35409} &:= \frac{1 - (2 - (8 + (7 - 6)))}{35 - (4 - (0 - 9))} := \frac{1 + (2 + (8 + (7 - 6)))}{3 \times ((5 \times (4 - 0)) - 9)} := \frac{1 \times (2 \times (8 \times (7 - 6)))}{3 + (5 - (4 \times (0 - 9)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (2 + (8 + (7 + 6)))}{3 + (54 - (0 - 9))} := \frac{1 - (2 + (8 - (7 + 6)))}{3 - (5 - (4 - (0 - 9)))} := \frac{(1 + (28 - 7)) \times 6}{354 - (0 - 9)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((2 \times 87) + 6)}{((3 \times 5) + 40) \times 9} := \frac{1 \times (2 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6)))}{3 \times ((5^4 + 0) - 9)} := \frac{1 \times (2 - (8 - (7 \times 6)))}{((3 \times 5) - (4 - 0)) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{13095}{76824} &:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times ((0 \times 9) + 5))}{(7 \times (6 + (8 - 2))) + 4} := \frac{1 + (30 + (9 + 5))}{(76 - (8 + 2)) \times 4} := \frac{1 \times ((3 - (0 - 9)) \times 5)}{(7 \times (6 \times 8)) + (2^4)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (30 + (9 \times 5))}{(7 + (6 \times 8)) \times (2 \times 4)} := \frac{1 \times ((30 - 9) \times 5)}{7 \times ((6 + (8 \times 2)) \times 4)} := \frac{1 \times (3 \times ((09 \times 5)))}{768 + 24} \\ &:= \frac{130 + 95}{(7 + (6 \times 8)) \times 24} := \frac{1 + (309 + 5)}{7 \times ((68 - 2) \times 4)} := \frac{1 \times (30 \times (9 + 5))}{7 \times ((6 + 82) \times 4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{13095}{86427} &:= \frac{(1^{309}) \times 5}{8 - (6 - (4 + 27))} := \frac{(1 - 3) \times ((0 \times 9) - 5)}{(8 \times (6 + 4)) - (2 \times 7)} := \frac{1 \times (3 \times ((0 \times 9) + 5))}{8 + (64 + 27)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (3 + (0 - 9))) \times 5}{((8 + 6) \times (4^2)) + 7} := \frac{((1^3 + 0) + 9) \times 5}{(86 \times 4) - (2 \times 7)} := \frac{1 \times ((3 - (0 - 9)) \times 5)}{((8 \times 6) - 4) \times (2 + 7)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (3 - (0 - 9))) \times 5}{8 - (6 - 427)} := \frac{1 \times (3 \times ((09 \times 5)))}{864 + 27} := \frac{(1 + (3 - 0)) \times (9 \times 5)}{((8 \times 6) - 4) \times 27} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{13248}{57960} &:= \frac{1 \times (3 \times ((2^4) - 8))}{5 \times (7 \times (9 - (6 - 0)))} := \frac{1 - (3 - (2 + (4 \times 8)))}{(5 \times (7 + 9)) + 60} := \frac{1 \times (3 \times (24 + 8))}{(5 - (7 - 9)) \times 60} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (((3^2) + 4) \times 8)}{(5 \times 79) + 60} := \frac{1 \times ((32 \times 4) - 8)}{5 \times (7 \times (9 + (6 - 0)))} := \frac{1 \times (3 \times (2 \times 48))}{(5 + (7 + 9)) \times 60} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (3 \times (2^4))) \times 8}{5 \times (7^{9-6} + 0)} := \frac{1 \times ((3^2) \times 48)}{5 \times (7 \times (9 \times (6 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + 3) \times (24 \times 8)}{5 \times (7 \times (96 - 0))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13524}{87906} &:= \frac{1 \times (3 + (5 - (2 - 4)))}{8 + ((7 \times (9 - 0)) - 6)} := \frac{1 - (3 - ((5 \times 2) + 4))}{87 - (9 - (0 \times 6))} := \frac{1 - (3 - (52 + 4))}{8 + (7^9 - 06)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + (3 + (52 + 4))}{((8 \times 7) + (9 - 0)) \times 6} := \frac{1 + ((3 \times (5^2)) - 4)}{(87 - (9 - 0)) \times 6} := \frac{1 + (3 + (5 \times (2^4)))}{(8 - (7 - 90)) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times ((3 + (5^2)) \times 4)}{8 \times (7 + (90 - 6))} := \frac{1 \times (3 + (5 + (2 \times 4)))}{8 + ((7 + (9 - 0)) \times 6)} := \frac{1 \times ((35 + 2) \times 4)}{(8 \times 7) + 906} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13689}{24570} &:= \frac{(1^3) \times ((6 \times 8) - 9)}{(2 + (4 - 5)) \times 70} := \frac{1 \times (3 \times ((6 \times 8) - 9))}{(2 - (4 - 5)) \times 70} := \frac{(1 + 3) \times (6 + (8 \times 9))}{(2^4) \times (5 \times (7 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{13 \times ((6 \times 8) + 9)}{(24 - 5) \times 70} := \frac{(1 + (3 + (6 \times 8))) \times 9}{24 \times (5 \times (7 - 0))} := \frac{13 \times ((6 \times 8) - 9)}{((2 \times 4) + 5) \times 70} \\
 &:= \frac{13 + 689}{2 \times ((4 + 5) \times 70)} := \frac{(1 + 3) \times ((6 \times 8) - 9)}{2 \times (4 \times (5 \times (7 - 0)))} := \frac{1 + ((3^6) + 89)}{((2^4) + 5) \times 70} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14760}{39852} &:= \frac{1 - (4 - (7 + (6 - 0)))}{3 - (9 - (8 + (5^2)))} := \frac{1 - (4 + (7 - 60))}{3 \times (9 \times (8 - (5 - 2)))} := \frac{1 \times (4 + (76 - 0))}{(3 + 9) \times (8 + (5 \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{14 + (76 - 0)}{3 \times (9 \times ((8 - 5)^2))} := \frac{(1 - (4 - 7)) \times 60}{3 \times (9 \times (8 \times (5 - 2)))} := \frac{((1^4)^7) \times 60}{3 \times (9 \times ((8 - 5) \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + 4) \times (76 - 0)}{3 \times (9 \times ((8 \times 5) - 2))} := \frac{(14 - 7) \times 60}{3 \times (9 \times ((8 \times 5) + 2))} := \frac{((1^4) + 7) \times 60}{(3 \times (9 + (8 - 5)))^2} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14796}{32058} &:= \frac{1 \times (4 - (7 - (9 + 6)))}{3 + (20 - (5 - 8))} := \frac{((1 - (4 - 7)) \times 9) - 6}{(3 + (2 - 0)) \times (5 + 8)} := \frac{1 \times ((4 - (7 - 9)) \times 6)}{3 \times (2 \times ((05 + 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1^4) - (7 - (9 \times 6))}{(3 - (2 \times (0 - 5))) \times 8} := \frac{1 + (4 + (7 + 96))}{3 \times (20 + 58)} := \frac{(1 - (4 \times (7 - 9))) \times 6}{(3^2 + 0) \times (5 + 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (4 - (7 \times 9))) \times 6}{3 \times (20 \times (5 + 8))} := \frac{((1^4) + 7) \times 96}{(3 + 205) \times 8} := \frac{(1^{479}) \times 6}{(3 \times (2 - (0 - 5))) - 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15736}{90482} &:= \frac{1 + (5 + (7 - (3 + 6)))}{9 - (0 - (4 + (8 + 2)))} := \frac{1 + (5 - (7 - (3 + 6)))}{(9 \times (0 - 4)) + 82} := \frac{1 - (5 - (7 + (3 + 6)))}{9 + (0 - (4 - (8^2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + (5 + (7 - (3 - 6)))}{90 - (4 - (8 - 2))} := \frac{1 \times (5 + (7 + 36))}{(90 + 48) \times 2} := \frac{1 \times (5 + (73 - 6))}{9 \times ((048 - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (5 \times ((7 - 3) \times 6))}{((90 - 4) \times 8) + 2} := \frac{157 - (3 - 6)}{904 + (8 \times 2)} := \frac{1 + (5 - (7 - (3^6)))}{90 + (4^{8-2})} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16385}{72094} &:= \frac{1 - (6 + (3 - (8 + 5)))}{7 + (2 - (0 - (9 + 4)))} := \frac{(1 + (6 + (3 - 8))) \times 5}{(7^2 + 0) - (9 - 4)} := \frac{1 \times (6 + ((3 \times 8) + 5))}{7 \times ((2 \times (09)) + 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + (6 + (38 - 5))}{(7 \times 20) + (9 \times 4)} := \frac{1 + (6 + (3 + (8 \times 5)))}{7 + (209 + 4)} := \frac{((1 - 6) \times 3) + 85}{7 \times ((2 - (0 - 9)) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (6 - (38 \times 5))}{720 + 94} := \frac{(1 + (63 - 8)) \times 5}{7 \times ((20 \times 9) - 4)} := \frac{(1 + 6) \times (38 \times 5)}{7 \times (209 \times 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16758}{43092} &:= \frac{1 - ((6 - 7) \times (5 + 8))}{4 \times (3^{0 \times 9 + 2})} := \frac{1 - ((6 - (7 + 5)) \times 8)}{4 + (30 + 92)} := \frac{(1 - (6 - (7 + 5))) \times 8}{(4 \times (3 - (0 \times 9)))^2} \\
 &:= \frac{(1^6) + (75 + 8)}{4 \times (3 \times ((09 \times 2)))} := \frac{1 + ((6 \times (7 - 5)) + 8)}{43 - (0 - (9 + 2))} := \frac{1 + ((6 \times (7 \times 5)) - 8)}{430 + 92} \\
 &:= \frac{(1^6) - (7 - (5 + 8))}{4 + (3 - (0 - (9 + 2)))} := \frac{(16 + (7 + 5)) \times 8}{4 \times ((3 - (0 - 9))^2)} := \frac{(1 + 6) \times ((7 \times 5) + 8)}{43 \times ((09 \times 2))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17028}{49536} &:= \frac{(1^7 + 0) + (2 + 8)}{((4 + 9) \times (5 - 3)) + 6} := \frac{1 - (7 + (0 - 28))}{49 - (5 \times (3 - 6))} := \frac{17 - (0 - (2 \times 8))}{4 \times (9 - (5 \times (3 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + (70 - (2 \times 8))}{4 \times (9 - (5 - 36))} := \frac{1 + (70 - (2 - 8))}{4 \times (9 + (53 - 6))} := \frac{1 + (70 + 28)}{4 \times (9 \times (5 - (3 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times ((70 \times 2) - 8)}{(49 + (5 \times 3)) \times 6} := \frac{170 - (2 - 8)}{4 \times (9 + ((5^3) - 6))} := \frac{170 + 28}{4 \times ((9 + (5 \times 3)) \times 6)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17085}{64923} &:= \frac{1 + (7 + (0 - (8 - 5)))}{6 - (4 - (9 + (2^3)))} := \frac{1 \times (7 - (0 - (8 - 5)))}{6 + (4 \times (9 + (2 - 3)))} := \frac{1 \times (70 - (8 \times 5))}{6 \times (4 + (9 + (2 \times 3)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (7 - (0 \times 8))) \times 5}{(6 + (4 + 9)) \times (2^3)} := \frac{((1^7 + 0) + 8) \times 5}{(6 \times (4 \times (9 - 2))) + 3} := \frac{1 \times ((7 - (0 - 8)) \times 5)}{(6 \times (49 - 2)) + 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (7 \times (0 - 8))) \times 5}{((6 + (4 + 9))^2) \times 3} := \frac{(170 \times 8) + 5}{(64 \times (9^2)) + 3} := \frac{1 \times ((70 + 8) \times 5)}{6 \times (4 + ((9^2) \times 3))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17340}{65892} &:= \frac{(1^{73}) + (4 - 0)}{(6 - 5) \times (8 + (9 + 2))} := \frac{17 - (3 + (4 - 0))}{(6 \times (5 - (8 - 9))) + 2} := \frac{1 + (7 + (3 + (4 - 0)))}{6 - (5 - (8 \times (9 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times ((7 \times 3) + (4 - 0))}{6 + (5 - (8 - 92))} := \frac{(1^7) + (34 - 0)}{(6 + (5 + 8)) \times (9 - 2)} := \frac{(1^{73}) \times 40}{65 + (89 - 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1^7) \times (3 \times 40)}{6 \times (58 + (9 \times 2))} := \frac{(17 \times 3) + (4 - 0)}{(6 + (5 + 8)) \times (9 + 2)} := \frac{1 + (73 - (4 - 0))}{((6 \times 5) + 8) \times (9 - 2)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17829}{30564} &:= \frac{1 \times (7^{8+2-9})}{3 \times ((0 \times 56) + 4)} := \frac{1 \times (7 + ((8 \times 2) - 9))}{(3 \times (0 \times 5)) + (6 \times 4)} := \frac{1 \times (((7 + 8) \times 2) - 9)}{((3 \times (05)) - 6) \times 4} \\
 &:= \frac{17 + ((8 \times 2) + 9)}{3 - (0 - (5 + 64))} := \frac{1 - (7 - ((8^2) - 9))}{((3 \times (05)) + 6) \times 4} := \frac{(1^7) \times (82 + 9)}{3 \times ((056 - 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (7 \times (8 - (2 - 9)))}{3 \times ((056 + 4))} := \frac{1 \times (7 \times ((8 \times 2) + 9))}{30 \times (5 \times (6 - 4))} := \frac{(1 - 7) \times (8 \times (2 - 9))}{((30 \times 5) - 6) \times 4}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17829}{56034} &:= \frac{1 \times (7^{8+2-9})}{56 + (0 - 34)} := \frac{1 \times (7 + ((8 \times 2) - 9))}{(5 + (6 - (0 \times 3))) \times 4} := \frac{1 \times (((7 + 8) \times 2) - 9)}{5 + (60 - (3 - 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + 7) \times 8) - 29}{5 \times ((6 \times (03)) + 4)} := \frac{17 + ((8 \times 2) + 9)}{(5 + (6 - 0)) \times (3 \times 4)} := \frac{17 \times ((8 \times 2) - 9)}{(5 + (6 - 0)) \times 34} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (7 \times (8 + (2 \times 9)))}{560 + (3 \times 4)} := \frac{178 + (2 + 9)}{560 + 34} := \frac{1 \times (7 \times ((8 - 2) \times 9))}{((5 \times 60) - 3) \times 4}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18063}{74259} &:= \frac{1 + (8 - (0 \times 63))}{7 - (4 - (25 + 9))} := \frac{1 + (8 - (0 - (6 + 3)))}{7 + (4 + ((2 + 5) \times 9))} := \frac{(1 + (8 - 0)) \times 63}{7 \times ((42 - 5) \times 9)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + (80 - (6 \times 3))}{7 - ((4 - (2^5)) \times 9)} := \frac{(1 + (8 - 0)) \times (6 + 3)}{(7 + ((4 + 2) \times 5)) \times 9} := \frac{180 \times (6 + 3)}{74 \times (2 \times (5 \times 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{18 \times (063)}{74 \times ((2 + 5) \times 9)} := \frac{180 + (6 + 3)}{(7 - 4) \times 259} := \frac{1 \times (8 \times (063))}{74 \times (2 \times (5 + 9))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18360}{95472} &:= \frac{1 \times (8 + (3 - (6 - 0)))}{9 - ((5 \times (4 - 7)) - 2)} := \frac{(1^8) + (3 + (6 - 0))}{(9 - 5) \times (4 + (7 + 2))} := \frac{18 + (3 - (6 - 0))}{9 + ((5 \times 4) + (7^2))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (8 \times (3 - (6 - 0)))}{(9 \times (5 + 4)) + (7^2)} := \frac{1 \times ((8 - 3) \times (6 - 0))}{((9 + 5) \times (4 + 7)) + 2} := \frac{1 + (8 + (36 - 0))}{9 - (5 \times (4 - (7^2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{18 - (3 - 60)}{((9 + 5) \times (4 \times 7)) - 2} := \frac{(1^8) \times (3 \times 60)}{9 \times ((5 + 47) \times 2)} := \frac{(18 + 3) \times 60}{(95 - 4) \times 72}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19350}{24768} &:= \frac{1 + (9 + (3 \times (5 - 0)))}{2^{4+(7-6)^8}} := \frac{((1+9)^3) + 50}{(2^4) \times (76 + 8)} := \frac{(1^{93}) \times 50}{2 \times (4 \times ((7-6) \times 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (9 + 3)) \times 50}{2 \times (4 \times ((7 + 6) \times 8))} := \frac{(1^9) \times (3 \times 50)}{2 \times ((4 \times 7) + 68)} := \frac{((1^9) + 3) \times 50}{(2^{4+7-6}) \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{19 \times (3 \times 50)}{(2 + 4) \times (76 \times 8)} := \frac{1 \times ((9 - 3) \times 50)}{(2 + (4 + (7 \times 6))) \times 8} := \frac{(1 + (9 - 3)) \times 50}{((2 + 4) \times 76) - 8} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19357}{20846} &:= \frac{1 - ((9 - 3) \times (5 - 7))}{(2 \times ((08 - 4))) + 6} := \frac{1 - ((9 \times (3 - 5)) - 7)}{2 - (0 - ((8 \times 4) - 6))} := \frac{1 \times ((9 \times 3) + (5 + 7))}{((20 - 8) \times 4) - 6} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (9 - (3 + 57))}{2 - (0 - (8 + 46))} := \frac{1 \times (9 + ((3 + 5) \times 7))}{(2 \times ((08 \times 4))) + 6} := \frac{1 + ((9 - (3 - 5)) \times 7)}{(2 - (0 - (8 + 4))) \times 6} \\
 &:= \frac{1 \times (93 + (5 - 7))}{20 + (84 - 6)} := \frac{1 + (9 + ((3^5) + 7))}{(2^{08}) + (4 \times 6)} := \frac{193 - (5 - 7)}{(2^{08}) - 46} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19683}{24057} &:= \frac{(1 - (9 - (6 + 8))) \times 3}{2 \times (4 - ((0 \times 5) - 7))} := \frac{1 + (9 + (6 + (8 + 3)))}{2 - (4 + (0 - (5 \times 7)))} := \frac{(1 + (9 - (6 - 8))) \times 3}{2 + (40 - (5 - 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1^9) + (6 + 8)) \times 3}{2 - (4 + (0 - 57))} := \frac{1 \times (9^{6-8+3})}{(2 \times (4 - (0 - 5))) - 7} := \frac{1 - (9 - (68 + 3))}{(2 + (4 - (0 - 5))) \times 7} \\
 &:= \frac{1 - (9 - (6 + 83))}{2 + (40 + 57)} := \frac{1 \times ((9 + (6 \times 8)) \times 3)}{2 + ((40 \times 5) + 7)} := \frac{1 \times (9 - 6)^{8-3}}{240 + 57} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{21368}{50749} &:= \frac{(2 \times (1 - (3 - 6))) + 8}{50 - (7 - (4 - 9))} := \frac{2 \times (1 - (3 - (6 + 8)))}{((5 - (0 - 7)) \times 4) + 9} := \frac{(2 - (1 \times (3 - 6))) \times 8}{5 \times (((07 \times 4) - 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (36 - 8))}{50 + (74 + 9)} := \frac{(2 - (1 - (3 \times 6))) \times 8}{(5 \times (074)) - 9} := \frac{(2 + (1 + (3 \times 6))) \times 8}{(50 \times 7) + 49} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + ((1 + 3) \times 6)) \times 8}{507 - (4 + 9)} := \frac{(2 + (1 + 36)) \times 8}{(50 + 7) \times (4 + 9)} := \frac{(21 - 3) \times (6 \times 8)}{(50 + 7) \times (4 \times 9)} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{21670}{95348} &:= \frac{(2 \times (1 \times 6)) - (7 - 0)}{9 + (5 - ((3 - 4) \times 8))} := \frac{2 + ((1^6) + (7 - 0))}{9 + (5 \times (3 - (4 - 8)))} := \frac{2 + (1 \times (6 + (7 - 0)))}{9 + (53 - (4 - 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{21 + (6 - (7 - 0))}{(9 - (5 - (3 + 4))) \times 8} := \frac{2 + (16 + (7 - 0))}{9 + (5 + (3 \times (4 \times 8)))} := \frac{2 - (1 + (6 - 70))}{9 + (5 + (34 \times 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times ((1^6) \times 70)}{((9^5-3) - 4) \times 8} := \frac{(2 \times (1 - 6)) + 70}{9 + (5 \times (3 + 48))} := \frac{21 - (6 - 70)}{9 + (5 \times ((3^4) - 8))} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23415}{60879} &:= \frac{2 + (3 - (4 + (1 - 5)))}{60 - ((8 \times 7) - 9)} := \frac{2 + (3 + ((4 - 1) \times 5))}{60 + (8 - (7 + 9))} := \frac{2 - (3 - (41 + 5))}{(6 - ((0 \times 8) - 7)) \times 9} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (3 \times (4 + (1 + 5)))}{60 + (87 + 9)} := \frac{(2 \times (34 + 1)) + 5}{60 + ((8 + 7) \times 9)} := \frac{2 \times (3 \times ((4 + 1) \times 5))}{6 \times (((08 \times 7) + 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (34 \times 1)) \times 5}{6 \times ((087 - 9))} := \frac{2 + ((3^{4+1}) - 5)}{608 + (7 + 9)} := \frac{(2^{3+4-1}) \times 5}{(60 - 8) \times (7 + 9)} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23490}{51678} &:= \frac{2 + (3 - (4 - (9 - 0)))}{5 + (16 - (7 - 8))} := \frac{(2 \times (3 \times 4)) - (9 - 0)}{(5 \times (1 - (6 - 7))) + 8} := \frac{(2 \times (3 + 4)) - (9 - 0)}{5 - (1 - (6 - (7 - 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 - (3 - (4 \times (9 - 0)))}{5 - (1 \times (6 - 78))} := \frac{2 + (34 + (9 - 0))}{5 + (16 + 78)} := \frac{2 \times (34 - (9 - 0))}{5 \times (1 + (6 + (7 + 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 - ((3 \times 4) - 90)}{((5 - 1) \times (6 \times 7)) + 8} := \frac{2 - (3 \times (4 - 90))}{516 + (7 \times 8)} := \frac{(2 - (3 - 4)) \times 90}{516 + 78}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23790}{61854} &:= \frac{2 \times (3 - (7 - (9 - 0)))}{6 + ((1^8) \times (5 \times 4))} := \frac{2 - (3 - (7 + (9 - 0)))}{((6 + (1^8)) \times 5) + 4} := \frac{23 - (7 - (9 - 0))}{((6 + 1) \times 8) + (5 + 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + (37 - (9 - 0))}{6 + (1 \times (8 \times (5 + 4)))} := \frac{(2 \times 3) + (79 - 0)}{61 + (8 \times (5 \times 4))} := \frac{2 \times ((3 + 7) \times (9 - 0))}{(61 \times 8) - (5 \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (3 + (7 + 90))}{(6 \times (1 + 85)) + 4} := \frac{23 + (7 + 90)}{6 \times (1 \times ((8 + 5) \times 4))} := \frac{(23 + 7) \times (9 - 0)}{(6 - (1 - 8)) \times 54}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{28134}{60957} &:= \frac{2 + (8 \times (1 - (3 - 4)))}{60 - (9 + (5 + 7))} := \frac{2 \times (8 + ((1^3) \times 4))}{(6 \times (09)) + (5 - 7)} := \frac{2 - (8 - (1 \times (3 \times 4)))}{6 - (0 - (9 + (5 - 7)))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (8 + (1 + (3 \times 4)))}{(6 \times ((09 + 5))) + 7} := \frac{(2 + (8 - (1 - 3))) \times 4}{6 - (0 - ((9 + 5) \times 7))} := \frac{2 \times ((8 + (1^3)) \times 4)}{6 \times (0 - (9 - (5 \times 7)))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + (8 + 134)}{6 \times (((09 \times 5) + 7))} := \frac{(2 + (8 - (1^3))) \times 4}{60 - (9 \times (5 - 7))} := \frac{2 + (8 \times (1 + 34))}{609 - (5 - 7)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{28193}{64075} &:= \frac{2 + (8 + (1 \times (9 + 3)))}{(6 + (4 - (0 \times 7))) \times 5} := \frac{(2 + (8 + (1^9))) \times 3}{((6 + (4 - 0)) \times 7) + 5} := \frac{2 + ((8 - 1) \times (9 - 3))}{(6 + (4 - 0))^{7-5}} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (8 + 1)) \times (9 - 3)}{(6 - (4 - 0)) \times 75} := \frac{28 + (1 \times 93)}{(6 \times 40) + (7 \times 5)} := \frac{2 \times ((8 \times (1 + 9)) - 3)}{(6 + (4 - 0)) \times (7 \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (8 + 1)) \times (9 \times 3)}{640 + (7 \times 5)} := \frac{((2^8) - (1 - 9)) \times 3}{6 \times (4 \times (075))} := \frac{(2 - (8 \times (1 - 9))) \times 3}{6 \times (40 + (7 \times 5))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29367}{45180} &:= \frac{2 + (9 + (3 + (6 - 7)))}{4 \times (5 \times (1^8 + 0))} := \frac{2 \times (93 - 67)}{4 - (5 - (1 + 80))} := \frac{2 - ((9 - (3 \times 6)) \times 7)}{(4 \times (5 \times 1)) + 80} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (9 + (36 + 7))}{4 \times (5 \times (1 \times (8 - 0)))} := \frac{2 \times (((9 + 3) \times 6) - 7)}{(4 \times 5) + 180} := \frac{(29 + 3) \times (6 + 7)}{(4 + (5 - 1)) \times 80} \\
 &:= \frac{(2^{9-3}) \times (6 + 7)}{4 \times ((5 - 1) \times 80)} := \frac{(29 - 3) \times (6 \times 7)}{((4 \times 5) + 1) \times 80} := \frac{(2^9) + ((3^6) + 7)}{4 \times ((5 + 1) \times 80)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29601}{75348} &:= \frac{2 + (9 - (6 \times (0 \times 1)))}{7 \times (5 + (3 + (4 - 8)))} := \frac{29 + (60 - 1)}{7 \times ((5 + (3 - 4)) \times 8)} := \frac{2 \times ((9 \times (6 - 0)) + 1)}{7 \times (5 + (3 + (4 \times 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{29 - (6 - (0 - 1))}{7 + (53 + (4 - 8))} := \frac{(2 + 9) \times (60 \times 1)}{((7 + 5)^3) - 48} := \frac{2 \times ((9 \times 60) - 1)}{7 \times ((53 - 4) \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + ((9 \times (6 - 0)) - 1)}{7 \times (5 + (3 + (4 + 8)))} := \frac{(2 + 9) \times (6 \times 01)}{7 \times ((5 - 3) \times (4 + 8))} := \frac{(2^9) + (6 \times (0 - 1))}{(((7 - 5) \times 3)^4) - 8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30186}{97524} &:= \frac{((3 - (0 - 1)) \times 8) - 6}{(9 \times (7 + 5)) - 24} := \frac{(30 \times 18) + 6}{9 \times (7 \times ((5 + 2) \times 4))} := \frac{3 \times (0 - (1 - (8 + 6)))}{9 \times (7 + (5 - (2 - 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{3 - (0 - (1 + (8 \times 6)))}{(9 - (7 - 5)) \times 24} := \frac{30 + (1 \times (8 \times 6))}{9 \times (7 + (5 + (2^4)))} := \frac{30 + (1 + 86)}{9 \times (7 \times ((5 \times 2) - 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(30 + (1 + 8)) \times 6}{9 \times (7 \times ((5 - 2) \times 4))} := \frac{301 - (8 - 6)}{(97 \times (5 \times 2)) - 4}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{31689}{45270} &:= \frac{3 - (1 \times (6 - (8 + 9)))}{(45 \times 2) - 70} := \frac{3 \times (1 \times (6 - (8 - 9)))}{(4 \times (5^2)) - 70} := \frac{(3 + 1) \times (6 - (8 - 9))}{4 \times (5 - (2 - (7 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (1 \times 6)) + (8 + 9)}{45 - (2 - (7 - 0))} := \frac{(31 \times 6) + (8 + 9)}{(4 \times 5) + 270} := \frac{3 \times (1 \times (68 + 9))}{((4 \times 5)^2) - 70} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times 16) - (8 - 9)}{(4 - (5 - 2)) \times 70} := \frac{3 \times (1 \times ((6 + 8) \times 9))}{4 \times (5 \times (27 - 0))} := \frac{31 + (6 + 89)}{4 \times (5 \times (2 + (7 - 0)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{30912}{48576} &:= \frac{(((3 \times (0 + 9)) + 1) \times 2)}{(4 + (85 - (7 - 6)))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 + (9 + 1))) - 2)}{(4 + (8 \times (5 \times (7 - 6))))} := \frac{((30 \times (9 - 1)) - 2)}{((4 \times (85 + 7)) + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(3 - (0 - (9 + (1 \times 2))))}{((4^{8-5}) - (7 \times 6))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (9 - (1 \times 2))))}{(3 \times (0 + (9 - (1 \times 2))))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (9 + 12)))}{(48 + (57 - 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(30 \times (91 \times 2))}{(4 + 8576)} := \frac{(30 + (9 + (1 + 2)))}{(48 + (5 + (7 + 6)))} := \frac{(309 - (1^2))}{(485 - (7 - 6))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{31976}{50248} &:= \frac{3 - (1 \times (9 - (7 + 6)))}{5 - (0 - (2 - (4 - 8)))} := \frac{3 \times ((1^{97}) + 6)}{(5^{-02+4}) + 8} := \frac{(3 \times (1 \times 9)) + (7 - 6)}{50 - (2 - (4 - 8))} \\ &:= \frac{3 - (1 + (9 - (7 \times 6)))}{5 - (0 - (2 + 48))} := \frac{(3 \times (1 \times (9 + 7))) - 6}{50 + (24 - 8)} := \frac{(3 \times 19) - (7 - 6)}{(5 \times ((02^4))) + 8} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (19 + 7)) + 6}{(50 \times 2) + (4 \times 8)} := \frac{3 + (1 + (9 + (7 - 6)))}{(5 \times ((02 + 4))) - 8} := \frac{(3 + (1 \times 9)) \times (7 \times 6)}{(50 \times (2^4)) - 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{32160}{97485} &:= \frac{32 \times (1 \times (6 - 0))}{97 \times ((4 \times 8)^5)} := \frac{32 \times (1^6 + 0)}{9 + (7 - (4 - 85))} := \frac{32 \times 160}{97 \times (4 \times (8 \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (2 \times (16 - 0))}{((9 + (7 \times 4)) \times 8) - 5} := \frac{(3 - 2) \times 160}{(9 + ((7 + 4) \times 8)) \times 5} := \frac{3 \times (2 \times (1 \times (6 - 0)))}{97 + 485} \\ &:= \frac{32 \times (1 + (6 - 0))}{(9 \times 74) + (8 + 5)} := \frac{32 \times (1 \times 60)}{97 \times ((4 + 8) \times 5)} := \frac{3 \times (2 \times (1 + (6 - 0)))}{97 \times (4 \times (8 - 5))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{32170}{54689} &:= \frac{3 + ((2 - 1) \times (7 - 0))}{((5 - 4)^6) \times (8 + 9)} := \frac{(3^{2+1}) - (7 - 0)}{(5^{4+6-8}) + 9} := \frac{3 \times (2 + (1 + (7 - 0)))}{5 - (46 \times (8 - 9))} \\ &:= \frac{32 + (1 + (7 - 0))}{5 + (4 + (68 - 9))} := \frac{3 - (2 + (1 - 70))}{(5 - (4 - 6)) \times (8 + 9)} := \frac{(3 - (2 - 1)) \times 70}{((5 \times 4) - 6) \times (8 + 9)} \\ &:= \frac{3 + (21 \times (7 - 0))}{(5 + (4 + 6)) \times (8 + 9)} := \frac{(3 - 2) \times 170}{(5 \times (4 \times (6 + 8))) + 9} := \frac{(3^2) \times 170}{(54 \times (6 \times 8)) + 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{32496}{71085} &:= \frac{3 + (2 - (4 - (9 + 6)))}{7 \times ((1^{08}) \times 5)} := \frac{32^{4-9+6}}{(7 - (1 + (0 - 8))) \times 5} := \frac{3 \times (2 - ((4 - 9) \times 6))}{7 \times (10 \times (8 - 5))} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times ((2^4) \times (9 - 6))}{7 \times ((1 - (0 - 8)) \times 5)} := \frac{3 \times (2 + ((4 + 9) \times 6))}{7 \times ((10 \times 8) - 5)} := \frac{(3 \times (2 \times 49)) - 6}{7 \times ((10 + 8) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{32 + (4 \times 96)}{7 \times (10 \times (8 + 5))} := \frac{32 \times (4 + 96)}{7 \times (10^{8-5})} := \frac{3 \times ((2 + 4) \times 96)}{7 \times (108 \times 5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{32571}{60489} &:= \frac{3 + (25 - (7 \times 1))}{(6 \times ((0 \times 4) + 8)) - 9} := \frac{3 + (2 + (5 \times (7 - 1)))}{(6 \times (0 - 4)) + 89} := \frac{3 \times (2 + (5 + (7 \times 1)))}{6 \times (0 - (4 - (8 + 9)))} \\ &:= \frac{3 - (25 - 71)}{6 + (0 - (4 - 89))} := \frac{3 \times (2 + (5 \times (7 + 1)))}{6 \times ((048 - 9))} := \frac{(3 + 25) \times (7 - 1)}{(60 \times 4) + (8 \times 9)} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + 25) \times (7 + 1)}{60 + (4 \times 89)} := \frac{(3^2) + (5 \times 71)}{604 + (8 \times 9)} := \frac{3 + (2 \times (5 \times (7 - 1)))}{60 + (48 + 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{34182}{75960} &:= \frac{3 \times (4 - (1^{82}))}{(7 \times 5) - (9 + (6 - 0))} := \frac{3^{4-1^{82}}}{7 + (59 - (6 - 0))} := \frac{3 - (4 - (1 \times (8^2)))}{7 \times (5 + (9 + (6 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{3 - (4 - (1 \times 82))}{(7 + (5 - 9)) \times 60} := \frac{(3 + 4) \times (18^2)}{(75 + 9) \times 60} := \frac{(3^{4+1^8}) \times 2}{(7 - 5) \times (9 \times 60)} \\ &:= \frac{(3^4) \times (1 + (8 - 2))}{(7 + (5 + 9)) \times 60} := \frac{(3^4) \times (18 \times 2)}{(7 + 5) \times (9 \times 60)} := \frac{(3^{4 \times 1}) \times (8^2)}{(7 + 5) \times 960} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{35802}{41769} &:= \frac{(3 - (5 - (8 - 0))) \times 2}{4 + (1 \times (7 - (6 - 9)))} := \frac{3 + (5 + (8 - (0 - 2)))}{((4 + (1^7)) \times 6) - 9} := \frac{3 + (5 - (8 \times (0 - 2)))}{4 - ((1 + 7) \times (6 - 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (5 - (8 - 0)))^2}{41 + ((7 - 6)^9)} := \frac{3 - (5 - (8 - (0 \times 2)))}{4 - (1 - (7 + (6 - 9)))} := \frac{(3 + 5) \times (8 + (0 - 2))}{4 + (1 + ((7 \times 6) + 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{(35 - (8 - 0)) \times 2}{((4 + (1 + 7)) \times 6) - 9} := \frac{3 \times (5 \times (8 \times (02)))}{4 \times ((1^7) + 69)} := \frac{358 - (0 - 2)}{4 \times (1 \times (7 \times (6 + 9)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{36047}{81925} &:= \frac{(3 \times (6 - (0 \times 4))) - 7}{8 + (1 - (9 - 25))} := \frac{36 - (0 - (4 - 7))}{(8 + (1 \times (9 - 2))) \times 5} := \frac{3 - (6 + (0 - 47))}{(8 + (1 + (9 + 2))) \times 5} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (6 - 0)) \times (4 + 7)}{(8 + (1^9)) \times 25} := \frac{((3 \times (6 - 0)) + 4) \times 7}{((8 \times (1 \times 9)) - 2) \times 5} := \frac{3 \times (6 \times ((04 + 7)))}{(8 + (1 + (9^2))) \times 5} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + 60) \times (4 + 7)}{(8 - 1) \times (9 \times 25)} := \frac{(3^6 + 0) \times (4 + 7)}{81 \times (9 \times 25)} := \frac{36 \times ((04 + 7))}{(81 + 9) \times (2 \times 5)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{37152}{80496} &:= \frac{3 + (7 + (1 + (5^2)))}{(8 + (0 - (4 - 9))) \times 6} := \frac{3 \times (7 + (1 \times (5 + 2)))}{80 - (4 - (9 + 6))} := \frac{3 - (7 - (1 \times 52))}{8 - ((0 \times 4) - 96)} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times (7 + (15 - 2))}{80 - (4 - (9 \times 6))} := \frac{371 + (5 + 2)}{804 + (9 + 6)} := \frac{3 \times ((71 - 5) \times 2)}{804 + (9 \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times ((7 + (1^5))^2)}{(80 \times 4) + 96} := \frac{37 \times ((1 + 5)^2)}{(80 \times (4 \times 9)) + 6} := \frac{3 \times (71 + (5^2))}{8 \times (((04 + 9) \times 6))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{37650}{48192} &:= \frac{3 + ((7 \times 6) + (5 - 0))}{4 \times (8 + (1 + (9 - 2)))} := \frac{3 + (7 + (65 - 0))}{4 \times (8 \times ((1^9) + 2))} := \frac{(3 - (7 - 6)) \times 50}{4 \times ((8 - (1 - 9)) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + 7) \times (65 - 0)}{4 + ((8 + 1) \times 92)} := \frac{(3 + (7 - 6)) \times 50}{4 \times (8 \times (1 + (9 - 2)))} := \frac{((3 \times 7) - 6) \times 50}{48 \times ((1 + 9) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (7 + 6)) \times 50}{4^{8-1^9-2}} := \frac{(3 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 - 0))}{4 \times (8 \times (1 + (9 + 2)))} := \frac{((3 \times 7) + 6) \times 50}{(4 + 8)^{1^9+2}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{38210}{64957} &:= \frac{3 + (8 - (2 - (1 - 0)))}{6 + (4 + (9 + (5 - 7)))} := \frac{(3 \times (8 + 2)) - 10}{6 + (4 \times (9 + (5 - 7)))} := \frac{(3 \times (8 + 2)) + 10}{6 - (4 - (9 + 57))} \\
 &:= \frac{38 + (2 + 10)}{64 + (9 + (5 + 7))} := \frac{3 \times (8 + (2 + 10))}{((6 + (4 + 9)) \times 5) + 7} := \frac{((3 + 8)^2) - (1 - 0)}{6 \times ((4 \times 9) + (5 - 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times ((8 - 2) \times 10)}{6 \times (49 - (5 - 7))} := \frac{3 \times ((8 + 2) \times 10)}{((6 - 4)^9) + (5 - 7)} := \frac{(38 - 2) \times 10}{6 \times (4 + ((9 + 5) \times 7))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41063}{59728} &:= \frac{4 + (10 - (6 - 3))}{(5 \times (9 - 7)) - (2 - 8)} := \frac{4 - (1 \times (0 - (6 \times 3)))}{5 - (9 \times (7 - (2 + 8)))} := \frac{(4 + (1 - (0 - 6))) \times 3}{(5 - (9 - 7)) \times (2 \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{41 - (0 - (6 - 3))}{((5 \times (9 - 7)) - 2) \times 8} := \frac{4 - (1 + (0 - 63))}{5 + (97 + (2 - 8))} := \frac{4 + (10 + 63)}{5 + (97 + (2 + 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 - (1 - 0))^6) - 3}{(59 + 7) \times (2 \times 8)} := \frac{4 - (1 \times (0 - (6^3)))}{5 + (9 \times (7 + 28))} := \frac{410 + 63}{(5 + (9 + 72)) \times 8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{46152}{98073} &:= \frac{4 + (6 + (1 - (5 - 2)))}{9 + (8 - (0 \times 73))} := \frac{4 - (6 - (1 + (5^2)))}{(9 + (8 - (0 \times 7))) \times 3} := \frac{4 \times (6 - (1 - (5 - 2)))}{9 - ((8 \times (0 - 7)) - 3)} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (6 + (1 + (5 - 2)))}{9 + (80 - (7 - 3))} := \frac{4 \times (6 - (1 - (5 + 2)))}{98 - (0 - (7 - 3))} := \frac{4 \times (6 + (1 + (5 + 2)))}{98 - (0 - (7 \times 3))} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times ((6 - (1 - 5)) \times 2)}{(9 + (8 - 0)) \times (7 + 3)} := \frac{4 \times (6 + (1 + (5^2)))}{9 - (80 - (7^3))} := \frac{4 \times (6 \times (1 \times (5 + 2)))}{(9 + (8 - 0)) \times (7 \times 3)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{46782}{91530} &:= \frac{4 + (6 + (7 + (8 - 2)))}{9 + (1 + (5 + 30))} := \frac{4 + ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 2)}{(9 - (1 + 5)) \times 30} := \frac{4 - (6 - (7 + (8^2)))}{9 + (1 + (5^3 + 0))} \\ &:= \frac{((4 + (6 + 7)) \times 8) + 2}{9 \times ((1^5) \times 30)} := \frac{(4 + 6) \times (7 + (8 \times 2))}{(9 + (1 + 5)) \times 30} := \frac{(4 + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 - 2)}{9 + (1 + 530)} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times ((6 \times (7 + 8)) + 2)}{(9 + 15) \times 30} := \frac{467 + (8 \times 2)}{915 + 30} := \frac{46 + 782}{9 \times ((1 + 5) \times 30)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{49320}{51786} &:= \frac{4 \times (9 + (3 - (2 - 0)))}{(5 + (1 - (7 - 8))) \times 6} := \frac{(4 + (9 - 3))^2 + 0}{5 \times (1 \times (7 + (8 + 6)))} := \frac{(4 + (9 - 3)) \times (2 - 0)}{5 + ((1 + 7) \times (8 - 6))} \\ &:= \frac{((4 \times 9) - 3) \times 20}{5 + ((1 + 7) \times 86)} := \frac{4 \times (9 \times (3 + (2 - 0)))}{5 + (178 + 6)} := \frac{(4 + (9 - 3)) \times 20}{5 \times (1 - (7 - (8 \times 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (9 + (3 \times (2 - 0)))}{5 + (((1 + 7) \times 8) - 6)} := \frac{(4 + (9 + 3)) \times 20}{(5 - 1) \times (78 + 6)} := \frac{4 \times ((9 - 3) \times 20)}{(5 + (1 + 78)) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{53780}{91426} &:= \frac{5 \times (3 + (7 - (8 - 0)))}{9 + (1 \times (4 - (2 - 6)))} := \frac{5 \times (3 - (7 - (8 - 0)))}{9 - ((1^4) - 26)} := \frac{(5 - 3) \times (7 + (8 - 0))}{9 + ((1 + (4 + 2)) \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(5 \times (3 - 7)) + 80}{(9 + (1 \times (4 \times 2))) \times 6} := \frac{5 \times (3 + (7 + (8 - 0)))}{9 \times (1 - (4 \times (2 - 6)))} := \frac{(5^3) - (7 + (8 - 0))}{91 + ((4^2) \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + (3 + 7)) \times (8 - 0)}{(9 + ((1 + 4)^2)) \times 6} := \frac{(5 - (3 - 7)) \times 80}{9 \times (142 - 6)} := \frac{5 \times ((3 + 7) \times (8 - 0))}{(9 + 1) \times (4 + (2^6))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{61398}{75042} &:= \frac{6 + (1 + (3 + (9 + 8)))}{(7 \times (5 - (0 \times 4))) - 2} := \frac{6 \times (1 \times (3 - (9 - 8)))}{7 - (5 + (0 - 42))} := \frac{61 + (3 - (9 - 8))}{7 \times (5 - (0 - (4 + 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (13 - (9 - 8))}{7 + ((5 - (0 - 4))^2)} := \frac{6 + (1 \times (3 + (9 \times 8)))}{7 + (50 + 42)} := \frac{6 \times (1 + (3 + (9 + 8)))}{7 \times ((5 \times (04)) + 2)} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (1 + (39 + 8))}{(7 \times 50) + (4 - 2)} := \frac{6 \times (1 + (3 + 98))}{750 - (4 - 2)} := \frac{(6 + (1 \times 3)) \times (9 \times 8)}{750 + 42} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{63954}{87210} &:= \frac{6 - (3 - (9 - (5 - 4)))}{8 + (7 \times (2 - 1 + 0))} := \frac{6 + ((3 \times (9 - 5)) + 4)}{(8 - (7 - 2)) \times 10} := \frac{6 + (3 \times (9 \times (5 - 4)))}{(8 + 7) \times (2 + (1 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{63 - (9 - (5 - 4))}{87 - (2 + 10)} := \frac{6 - (3 - (9 + 54))}{8 + (72 + 10)} := \frac{(((6 - 3) \times 9) - 5) \times 4}{8 \times (7 - (2 - 10))} \\ &:= \frac{63 + (95 - 4)}{(8 - 7) \times 210} := \frac{6 \times (3 + (9 + 54))}{((8 \times 7) - 2) \times 10} := \frac{6 \times (((3 \times 9) - 5) \times 4)}{8 \times ((7 + 2) \times 10)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{69174}{82350} &:= \frac{6 - (9 + ((1 - 7) \times 4))}{8 + (2 + (3 \times (5 - 0)))} := \frac{6 \times (9 + (1 - (7 - 4)))}{8 - ((2^3) - 50)} := \frac{6 \times (9 + ((1^7) + 4))}{(8 - (2 \times 3)) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{6 + (9 \times ((1 + 7) \times 4))}{(8 + (2 - 3)) \times 50} := \frac{6 \times (91 - (7 \times 4))}{(8 - (2 - 3)) \times 50} := \frac{6 + (9 \times (1 \times 74))}{(8 + (2^3)) \times 50} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (9 + (1 + (7 + 4)))}{(8 - (2 + 3)) \times 50} := \frac{6 \times ((9 + 1) \times (7 \times 4))}{8 \times ((2 + 3) \times 50)} := \frac{6 \times ((91 - 7) \times 4)}{8 \times (2 \times (3 \times 50))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{72810}{94653} &:= \frac{(7 + (2 - 8)) \times 10}{9 - (4 - (6 + (5 - 3)))} := \frac{((7 - 2) \times 8) - 10}{(9 + (4 \times (6 - 5))) \times 3} := \frac{(7^2) - (8 + (1 - 0))}{9 - (4 + (6 - 53))} \\ &:= \frac{((7 - 2) \times 8) + 10}{9 + (4 \times (6 + (5 + 3)))} := \frac{7 \times (2 + (8 \times (1 - 0)))}{(9 \times (4 \times 6)) - (5^3)} := \frac{(7 \times (2 + 8)) + 10}{(9 + 4) \times (6 + (5 - 3))} \\ &:= \frac{7 + (2 + (81 - 0))}{9 \times (4 - (6 - (5 \times 3)))} := \frac{7 \times (2 + (8 + 10))}{(9 + 4) \times (6 + (5 + 3))} := \frac{((7^2) - 8) \times 10}{9 + (4 \times (6 + (5^3)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{7506}{123849} &:= \frac{7 - (5 - (0 \times 6))}{1 + (2 \times (3 + (8 - (4 - 9))))} := \frac{7 + (5 + (0 - 6))}{1 + (2 + (3 + (84 + 9)))} := \frac{7 - (5 + (0 - 6))}{1 + (23 + ((8 + 4) \times 9))} \\ &:= \frac{7 + (5 - (0 \times 6))}{1 \times ((2 - ((3 - 8) \times 4)) \times 9)} := \frac{7 + (5 - (0 - 6))}{(1 - (2 - (38 - 4))) \times 9} := \frac{7 \times (50 + 6)}{12 \times ((3 + 8) \times 49)} \\ &:= \frac{(7 - (5 - 0))^6}{(1 + 23) \times (8 + (4 \times 9))} := \frac{(7 + (5 - 0)) \times 6}{12 + (3 \times (8 \times 49))} := \frac{7 \times (5 \times (06))}{((1^2) + 384) \times 9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8937}{104265} &:= \frac{8 - (9 + (3 - 7))}{1 \times ((04 + (26 + 5)))} := \frac{8 + (9 - (3 - 7))}{(1 - (0 - (4 \times (2 \times 6)))) \times 5} := \frac{8 + (9 + (3 + 7))}{((1 - (0 - 4)) \times (2^6)) - 5} \\ &:= \frac{8 - (9 - 37)}{10 \times (42 \times (6 - 5))} := \frac{8 + ((9 \times 3) + 7)}{10 + ((4^2) \times (6 \times 5))} := \frac{(8 \times 9) - (3 \times 7)}{((10^4 - 2) \times 6) - 5} \\ &:= \frac{8 + (9 + 37)}{10 \times (4 + ((2^6) - 5))} := \frac{8 - (9 - (3 + 7))}{(1 - (0 - 4)) \times (26 - 5)} := \frac{8 + (93 + 7)}{1 \times ((042 \times (6 \times 5)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9675}{123840} &:= \frac{9 - (6 - (7 - 5))}{(1 + (23 - 8)) \times (4 - 0)} := \frac{(9 + 6) \times (7 \times 5)}{1 \times ((2^3) \times 840)} := \frac{9 - (6 - (7 + 5))}{1 \times (2 \times (3 \times (8 \times (4 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 + 6) \times (7 - 5)}{1 \times ((2^3) \times (8 + 40))} := \frac{9 + (6 + 75)}{(1 + 23) \times (8 + 40)} := \frac{(9 + 6) \times 7 - 5}{(1 + (23 + 8)) \times 40} \\ &:= \frac{(9 + (6 + 7)) \times 5}{(12^3) - (8 \times 40)} := \frac{(9 - 6) \times 75}{(1 + (2^3)) \times (8 \times 40)} := \frac{9 + (6 + (7 \times 5))}{(1 + (23 - 8)) \times 40} \end{aligned}$$

• Four Digit's Numerator

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{3024}{185976} &:= \frac{((3 - (0 - 2)) \times 4)}{((18 \times (5 + (9 \times 7))) + 6)} := \frac{((3 \times (0 + 2)) - 4)}{((18 \times 5) - (9 - (7 \times 6)))} := \frac{((3 + (0 - 2)) \times 4)}{(((1 + (8 - 5)) \times (9 \times 7)) - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{((30 \times 2) + 4)}{((1 + (8 \times 5)) \times ((9 + 7) \times 6))} := \frac{(3 \times ((0 \times 2) + 4))}{(1 + (8 + ((5 - (9 - 7))^6)))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 - (2 - 4)))}{(1 - (8 \times (5 - (9 + (7 \times 6)))))} \\ &:= \frac{(30 - (2^4))}{(1 + (859 + (7 - 6)))} := \frac{(30 + (2 \times 4))}{((1 + (8 \times 5)) \times ((9 \times 7) - 6))} := \frac{(30 + (2^4))}{((1 + (8 \times 5)) \times ((9 \times 7) + 6))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{3195}{276048} &:= \frac{((3 - (1^9)) \times 5)}{(2 \times ((7 \times 60) + (4 + 8)))} := \frac{((3 \times (1 + 9)) - 5)}{((2 + ((7 + 60) \times 4)) \times 8)} := \frac{((3 \times (1 \times 9)) \times 5)}{(((2 + 7) \times 6)^{-04+8})} \\ &:= \frac{((3 + (1 \times 9)) \times 5)}{(27 \times (6 \times (0 + (4 \times 8))))} := \frac{((3 + (1^9)) \times 5)}{(27 \times (60 - (4 - 8)))} := \frac{((3 - 1) \times (9 \times 5))}{(27 \times (6 \times (0 + 48)))} \\ &:= \frac{((31 + 9) \times 5)}{((2 + 7) \times (60 \times (4 \times 8)))} := \frac{(3 \times (1 \times (9 \times 5)))}{((2 + 7) \times (6^{-04+8}))} := \frac{(3 \times (1 + (9 - 5)))}{(27 \times (6 \times ((0 \times 4) + 8)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{3916}{207548} &:= \frac{((3 \times 9) - (1 + 6))}{(20 \times (7 + (54 - 8)))} := \frac{((3 + 9) \times 16)}{((207 + 5) \times 48)} := \frac{(3 - (9 - (1 + 6)))}{((2 \times (0 \times 7)) + (5 + 48))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 - (9 \times (1 - 6)))}{((207 + 5) \times (4 + 8))} := \frac{(3 \times (9 - (1^6)))}{((2 \times (0 + (7 + (5^4)))) + 8)} := \frac{(3 \times (9 \times (1^6)))}{((20 + 7) \times (5 + 48))} \\ &:= \frac{(3^{9-1-6})}{((2 - (0 - 7)) \times (5 + 48))} := \frac{(3 + (9 \times (1^6)))}{(((20^7) \times 5) + (4 - 8))} := \frac{(3 + (9 + (1^6)))}{((20 - 7) \times (5 + 48))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{3918}{207654} &:= \frac{(3 \times (9 + 1)) - 8}{(2 \times (0 - ((7 \times 6) - (5^4))))} := \frac{((3 \times (9 - 1)) - 8)}{((2 - (0 - (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) \times 4)} := \frac{(3 - (9 - (1 \times 8)))}{(2 \times (0 - (7 - (6 + 54))))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 - (9 - (1 + 8)))}{(207 + (6 - 54))} := \frac{(3 - (9 + (1 - 8)))}{(2 - (0 - (7 + ((6 + 5) \times 4))))} := \frac{(3 + (9 - (1 \times 8)))}{(207 + (6 - (5 - 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (9 + (1 \times 8)))}{(((20 \times (7 + 6)) + 5) \times 4)} := \frac{(3 + (9 + (1^8)))}{((2^{0 \times 7 + 6}) + (5^4))} := \frac{(39 \times (1^8))}{(2076 - (5 + 4))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4068}{137295} &:= \frac{((4 - (0 - 6)) \times 8)}{((((1 + 3) \times 7) + (2^9)) \times 5)} := \frac{((4 \times (0 + 6)) + 8)}{((1 + ((3 \times 7) + 2)) \times (9 \times 5))} := \frac{(4 - ((0 \times 6) - 8))}{((1 + (3 + (7 \times (2 + 9)))) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - (0 - (6 \times 8)))}{(1 \times ((37 + 2) \times (9 \times 5)))} := \frac{(4 - (0 \times 68))}{(1 + (3 + ((7 \times (2 \times 9)) + 5)))} := \frac{(4 \times (0 - (6 - 8)))}{(1 \times (3 \times ((7 + (2 + 9)) \times 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (0 + (6 + 8)))}{(1 \times (3 \times (7 \times (2 \times (9 \times 5)))))} := \frac{(4^{-06+8})}{(1 \times (3 \times ((7 + 29) \times 5)))} := \frac{(40 + 68)}{((1^3) \times (729 \times 5))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4158}{307692} &:= \frac{(((4 + 1) \times 5) + 8)}{((30 + 7) \times (6 \times (9 + 2)))} := \frac{(4 - ((1^5)^8))}{(3 \times (0 + (7 + (69 - 2))))} := \frac{(4 - (1 + (5 - 8)))}{(3 + ((0 - (7 \times (6 - 9)))^2))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (15 - 8))}{((30 + 7) \times ((6 \times 9) + 2))} := \frac{(4 \times 1^{58})}{((30 \times 7) - (6 - 92))} := \frac{(4 + ((1^5) \times 8))}{((30 + 7) \times (6 + (9 \times 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (1 \times (5 - 8)))}{(3 - ((0 \times 7) - (69 + 2)))} := \frac{(4 + (1 + (5 - 8)))}{(3 - (0 - (7 + (69 \times 2))))} := \frac{(41 + (5 + 8))}{((30 + 7) \times (6 \times (9 \times 2)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4308}{296175} &:= \frac{((4 - (3 - 0)) \times 8)}{((2 + (9 \times (6 - (1 - 7)))) \times 5)} := \frac{((4^3 + 0) + 8)}{((2 + 9) \times (6 \times (1 \times 75)))} := \frac{((4^3 + 0) - 8)}{(2 + ((9 \times (61 \times 7)) + 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - (3 \times (0 \times 8)))}{((2 + ((9 \times 6) - (1^7))) \times 5)} := \frac{(4 - (3 \times (0 - 8)))}{((2 + ((9 \times 6) - 1)) \times (7 \times 5))} := \frac{(4 \times (3 - (0 \times 8)))}{(((2 \times 9) - (6 + 1)) \times 75)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (3 - (0 - 8)))}{((2 + ((9 \times 6) - 1))^{7-5})} := \frac{(4 \times (30 - 8))}{(2 \times (((9 \times 6) + 1)^{7-5}))} := \frac{(4 + (30 \times 8))}{(29 - (61 - (7^5)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4309}{267158} &:= \frac{((4 - (3 - 0)) \times 9)}{(2 \times (6 - (7 \times (1 - (5 \times 8)))))} := \frac{((4 \times (3 - 0)) + 9)}{((2 \times 671) - (5 \times 8))} := \frac{((4 \times (3 - 0)) - 9)}{((26 \times 7) + (1 - (5 - 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - (3 - (0 \times 9)))}{(2 - (6 - (7 + (1 + 58))))} := \frac{(4 - (3 \times (0 \times 9)))}{(2 \times ((6 \times (7 + 15)) - 8))} := \frac{(4 - (3 \times (0 - 9)))}{(2 + (6 \times ((7 + 1) \times (5 \times 8))))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - (3 + (0 - 9)))}{((2 \times 6) + ((71 + 5) \times 8))} := \frac{(4 + (3 - (0 \times 9)))}{(((2^6) + 7) \times (1 + 5)) + 8} := \frac{(4 + (3 - (0 - 9)))}{(2 + (6 \times (7 + 158)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4328}{170956} &:= \frac{(((4 - 3)^2) \times 8)}{(((1 + (70 - 9)) \times 5) + 6)} := \frac{((4 - (3 - 2)) \times 8)}{(((17 \times (0 + 9)) + 5) \times 6)} := \frac{((4 \times (3 \times 2)) - 8)}{(1 + ((70 \times 9) - (5 - 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{((4^3) - (2 \times 8))}{((1 - (7 \times (0 - (9 \times 5)))) \times 6)} := \frac{((4 + 3) \times (2 \times 8))}{(1 \times ((70 + 9) \times 56))} := \frac{(4 - ((3 \times 2) - 8))}{(((1 - (7 + (0 - 9)))^5) - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - (3 \times (2 - 8)))}{(1 \times ((70 + 9) \times (5 + 6)))} := \frac{(4 + ((3 \times 2) + 8))}{(1 + (709 - (5 - 6)))} := \frac{(4 + ((3 \times 2) - 8))}{(((1 + (7 - (0 - 9))) \times 5) - 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4503}{279186} &:= \frac{((4 + (5 - 0)) \times 3)}{(279 \times ((1^8) \times 6))} := \frac{((4 + (5 - 0))^3)}{(27 \times (9 \times 186))} := \frac{((4 - 5) \times (0 - 3))}{(2 + (7 - (9 - 186)))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - (5 \times (0 \times 3)))}{(2 \times (7 - (9 \times (1 - (8 + 6)))))} := \frac{(4 - (5 \times (0 - 3)))}{(2 + (7 \times ((9 \times 18) + 6)))} := \frac{(4 - (5 + (0 - 3)))}{(2 \times ((7 \times (9 - (1^8))) + 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (5 - (0 \times 3)))}{(279 \times (1 \times (8 - 6)))} := \frac{(4 + (5 - (0 - 3)))}{(2 \times (((7 \times (9 + 1)) - 8) \times 6))} := \frac{(4 + (5 + (0 - 3)))}{((2 \times (7 \times (9 + 18))) - 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4589}{367120} &:= \frac{((4 - (5 - 8)) \times 9)}{(36 \times (7 \times (1 \times 20)))} &:= \frac{((4 \times 5) - (8 + 9))}{((3 + (6 - 7)) \times 120)} &:= \frac{((4 \times 5) + (8 \times 9))}{((367 + 1) \times 20)} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 + (5 - 8))^9)}{((3 - (6 - (7 \times 1))) \times 20)} &:= \frac{((4 + 5) \times 89)}{(3 + 6) \times 7120} &:= \frac{(4 - (5 \times (8 - 9)))}{(3 \times ((6 + (7 - 1)) \times 20))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (5 - (8 - 9)))}{((3 + (6 + 7)) \times 120)} &:= \frac{(4 \times (5 + (8 - 9)))}{((3 \times (6 \times 71)) + (2 - 0))} &:= \frac{(4 + (5 - (8 - 9)))}{(((3 \times (6 + 7)) + 1) \times 20)} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4806}{127359} &:= \frac{((4 \times (8 - 0)) + 6)}{((127 \times (3 + 5)) - 9)} &:= \frac{(4 - (8 \times (0 \times 6)))}{(1 \times (((2 + (7 \times 3)) \times 5) - 9))} &:= \frac{(4 - (8 + (0 - 6)))}{(1 \times (2 + (7 + (35 + 9))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (8 + (0 - 6)))}{(((1 - (2 - 7))^3) + (5 - 9))} &:= \frac{(4^{8-06})}{(1 + (((2 \times (7 \times 3)) + 5) \times 9))} &:= \frac{(4 + (8 - (0 \times 6)))}{(1 \times (273 + (5 \times 9)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 - (0 - 6)))}{((1 + (2 + ((7 + 3) \times 5))) \times 9)} &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + (0 - 6)))}{(1 + (2 \times (7 + ((3 + 5) \times 9))))} &:= \frac{(4 + (80 - 6))}{(1 + (2 \times (((7 - 3)^5) + 9)))} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4806}{271539} &:= \frac{((4 \times (8 - 0)) - 6)}{((2 \times 715) + 39)} &:= \frac{((4 \times 80) - 6)}{((2 \times (71 \times (5^3))) - 9)} &:= \frac{((4 - 8) \times (0 - 6))}{(((2^7) - 15) \times (3 + 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (8 \times (0 \times 6)))}{(2 + (7 \times (1 \times (5 + (3 \times 9)))))} &:= \frac{(4 - (8 + (0 - 6)))}{((2 \times (7 + (1 + 53))) - 9)} &:= \frac{(4 + (8 - (0 \times 6)))}{(2 + (715 - 39))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 - (0 - 6)))}{(((2^7 \times 1) - (5 \times 3)) \times 9)} &:= \frac{(4 + (80 - 6))}{(((2^7) - 15) \times 39)} &:= \frac{(48 - (0 - 6))}{(((2^7) - 15) \times (3 \times 9))} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5069}{314278} &:= \frac{((5 \times (0 + 6)) + 9)}{((3 + (14 \times 2)) \times 78)} &:= \frac{(5 - ((0 \times 6) - 9))}{(3 + (1 + (4 \times (27 \times 8))))} &:= \frac{(5 - (0 - (6 + 9)))}{(((3 \times (1 \times 4)) \times 2) - 7) \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 - (0 - (6 - 9)))}{(3 + (1 + (4 \times (2 \times (7 + 8)))))} &:= \frac{(5 - (0 \times 69))}{(31 \times (4 + ((2 \times 7) - 8)))} &:= \frac{(5 \times ((0 \times 6) + 9))}{(31 \times ((4 + 2) \times (7 + 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times (0 - (6 - 9)))}{(31 \times ((4 - 2) \times (7 + 8)))} &:= \frac{(5 + (0 - (6 - 9)))}{((31 + (4 + 27)) \times 8)} &:= \frac{(50 + (6 - 9))}{(31 \times ((4^2) + 78))} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5078}{269134} &:= \frac{((5 \times (0 \times 7)) + 8)}{(2 \times ((6 \times (9 \times (1 + 3))) - 4))} &:= \frac{((5 \times (0 + 7)) + 8)}{(2 - (69 \times (1 - 34)))} &:= \frac{(5 - ((0 \times 7) - 8))}{((2 - 691) \times (3 - 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 - (0 - (7 + 8)))}{((2 \times (6 \times (91 - 3))) + 4)} &:= \frac{(5 - (0 - (7 - 8)))}{((2 + ((6 \times (9 \times 1)) - 3)) \times 4)} &:= \frac{(5 - (0 \times 78))}{(2 - (6 - ((91 \times 3) - 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times ((0 \times 7) + 8))}{((2 + (6 \times (91 - 3))) \times 4)} &:= \frac{(5 + (0 - (7 - 8)))}{(2 \times (6 + (9 \times (13 + 4))))} &:= \frac{(50 - (7 - 8))}{(2691 + (3 \times 4))} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5789}{463120} &:= \frac{((5 - (7 - 8)) \times 9)}{(4 \times ((6 + 3) \times 120))} &:= \frac{((5 \times (7 - 8)) + 9)}{(4 \times ((6 - (3 - 1)) \times 20))} &:= \frac{((5 \times 7) - (8 + 9))}{(4 \times (6 \times (3 \times (1 \times 20))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 + (7 - 8)) \times 9)}{(4 \times ((6^3 - 1) \times 20))} &:= \frac{((5 - 7) \times (8 - 9))}{((4 + (6 - (3 - 1))) \times 20)} &:= \frac{(5 - ((7 - 8) \times 9))}{(((4 + 6)^3) + 120)} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 - (7 \times (8 - 9)))}{(4 \times (6 \times ((3 - 1) \times 20)))} &:= \frac{(5 \times ((7 \times 8) + 9))}{((4 + (6^3 + 1)) \times 20)} &:= \frac{(5 + (7 + (8 - 9)))}{((4 \times ((6^3) - 1)) + 20)} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5802}{194367} &:= \frac{((5 \times (8 - 0)) + 2)}{(1 \times ((9 + (4 \times 3)) \times 67))} &:= \frac{((5 \times (8 - 0)) - 2)}{(19 \times (4 + ((3 + 6) \times 7)))} &:= \frac{((5 + (8 - 0)) \times 2)}{(((1^9) + (4 \times 3)) \times 67)} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 - 8) \times (0 - 2))}{((1 + (9 - (4 + 3))) \times 67)} &:= \frac{(5 \times (8 - (0 \times 2)))}{((19 + (4 - 3)) \times 67)} &:= \frac{(5 \times (8 \times (0 + 2)))}{(1 - (9 - ((4^3) \times (6 \times 7))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times (8 + (0 - 2)))}{(1 \times ((9 - 4) \times (3 \times 67)))} &:= \frac{(58 - (0 - 2))}{(1943 + 67)} &:= \frac{(58 + (0 - 2))}{((1 + (9 + (43 \times 6))) \times 7)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{6048}{137592} &:= \frac{((6 \times (0 \times 4)) + 8)}{(1 - (3 - ((7 - 5) \times 92)))} := \frac{((6 + (0 - 4)) \times 8)}{(1 + (3 \times ((7 - (5 - 9))^2)))} := \frac{(6 \times ((0 \times 4) + 8))}{(13 \times (7 \times (5 + (9 - 2))))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times (0 - (4 - 8)))}{(1 \times ((3 + 75) \times (9 - 2)))} := \frac{(6 \times (0 + (4 \times 8)))}{((1 + (37 \times 59)) \times 2)} := \frac{(60 - (4 \times 8))}{(1 + ((3 + (7 \times (5 \times 9))) \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{(60 - (4 - 8))}{(13 \times (7 \times (5 + (9 + 2))))} := \frac{(60 + (4 \times 8))}{(13 \times (7 \times (5 + (9 \times 2))))} := \frac{(60 - 48)}{((1 + (3 + (7 \times 5))) \times (9 - 2))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{6345}{291870} &:= \frac{(((6 - 3) \times 4) + 5)}{(2 + ((9 + 1) \times (8 + 70)))} := \frac{(6 - ((3 - 4) \times 5))}{(2 + (9 \times (1 \times (8 \times (7 - 0)))))} := \frac{(6 - (3 - (4 - 5)))}{((2 \times (9 \times (1 + 8))) - 70)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - (3 + (4 - 5)))}{(2 \times ((9 \times 18) - 70))} := \frac{(6 \times (3 + (4 - 5)))}{(2 - (9 + (1 - (8 \times 70))))} := \frac{(6 + ((3 \times 4) - 5))}{((2^9) - (1 - (87 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + ((3 - 4) \times 5))}{(2 \times (9 - (1 - (8 + (7 - 0)))))} := \frac{(6 + (3 - (4 - 5)))}{((2^9) + (18 - 70))} := \frac{(63 - (4 \times 5))}{(((2^{9-1}) \times 8) - 70)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{6723}{190485} &:= \frac{(((6 \times 7) - 2) \times 3)}{((1 + (9 - 0)) \times (4 \times 85))} := \frac{(((6 - (7 - 2)) \times 3)}{((1^{904}) \times 85)} := \frac{((6 \times (7 + 2)) + 3)}{(19 \times ((0 \times 4) + 85))} \\ &:= \frac{((6 \times (7 + 2)) - 3)}{((1 - (9 \times (0 - (4 \times 8)))) \times 5)} := \frac{((6 \times (7 - 2)) - 3)}{(1 \times (9 \times ((0 \times 4) + 85)))} := \frac{((6 + (7 + 2)) \times 3)}{((19 + (0 - 4)) \times 85)} \\ &:= \frac{(6^{7-2 \times 3})}{(1 + (9 - (0 - (4 \times (8 \times 5)))))} := \frac{(6 + (7 + (2 + 3)))}{((1 + (9 + (0 - 4))) \times 85)} := \frac{(6 + (7 + (2 - 3)))}{((1^9 + 0) \times (4 \times 85))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{6840}{192375} &:= \frac{((6 \times 8) + 40)}{((1 + (9 + 23)) \times 75)} := \frac{((6 \times 8) - 40)}{((1 + (9 - (2 - 37))) \times 5)} := \frac{((6 + 8) \times (4 - 0))}{(1 \times (9 \times ((2 + 3) \times (7 \times 5))))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times (8 - (4 - 0)))}{(1 \times (9 \times (((2^3) + 7) \times 5)))} := \frac{(6 \times (8 \times (4 - 0)))}{(1 \times (9 \times ((2^3) \times 75)))} := \frac{(6 \times (8 + (4 - 0)))}{(1 \times ((9 \times (2 + 3))^{7-5}))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times (8 + 40))}{((1 + (92 - 3))^{7-5})} := \frac{(6 \times (84 - 0))}{((192 - 3) \times 75)} := \frac{(68 - (4 - 0))}{((1 + (9 - 2)) \times (3 \times 75))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{6915}{428730} &:= \frac{(6 - (9 - (1 \times 5)))}{(4 \times (2 - (8 - (7 + 30))))} := \frac{(6 - (9 - (1 + 5)))}{(4 - (2 + (8 \times (7 - 30))))} := \frac{(6 - (9 + (1 - 5)))}{(4 - (2 \times (8 - (7 + 30))))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - (9 - 15))}{(4 \times (2 - (8 \times (7 - 30))))} := \frac{(6 \times (9 - (1 + 5)))}{(4 \times ((2^8) - (7 - 30)))} := \frac{(6 + (9 - (1 - 5)))}{((4 \times 287) + 30)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + (9 \times (1^5)))}{(((4^2) + (8 + 7)) \times 30)} := \frac{(6 + (9 + (1 + 5)))}{(42 \times (8 - (7 - 30)))} := \frac{(6 + (9 + 15))}{((4 + (2 + (8 \times 7))) \times 30)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{7295}{163408} &:= \frac{(((7 \times 2) - 9) \times 5)}{(16 \times (3 - (4 \times (0 - 8))))} := \frac{(((7 - 2) \times 9) - 5)}{(16 \times ((3 + (4 - 0)) \times 8))} := \frac{((7 \times 2) - (9 - 5))}{(1 \times ((6 - 34) \times (0 - 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{((7^2) - (9 - 5))}{(1 \times ((6 + (3 \times 40)) \times 8))} := \frac{((7 + (2 + 9)) \times 5)}{(1 \times (63 \times (4 \times (0 + 8))))} := \frac{(7 + ((2 \times 9) + 5))}{(1 \times (6 \times ((3 \times 40) - 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + (2 - (9 - 5)))}{((1 + (6 + (3 + (4 - 0)))) \times 8)} := \frac{(7 + (2 \times (9 + 5)))}{((1 + 6) \times ((3 \times 40) - 8))} := \frac{(7 + (2 \times (9 - 5)))}{(1 \times (6 \times ((3 + (4 - 0)) \times 8)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{7483}{261905} &:= \frac{((7 \times 4) - (8 - 3))}{(((2 + (6 + 1)) \times 90) - 5)} := \frac{((7 + (4 - 8)) \times 3)}{((2 + (6 - 1)) \times (9 \times (0 + 5)))} := \frac{(7 - ((4 - 8) \times 3))}{((2 + (6 - 1)) \times (90 + 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 - (4 - (8 + 3)))}{((2 + (6 + (1 \times 90))) \times 5)} := \frac{(7 - (4 - (8 - 3)))}{((2 + (6 \times (1 \times (9 - 0)))) \times 5)} := \frac{(7 + ((4 \times 8) - 3))}{((261 - (9 - 0)) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + (4 + (8 + 3)))}{(((2^6 \times 1) + 90) \times 5)} := \frac{(7 + (4 + (8 - 3)))}{((2 - (6 \times 19)) \times (0 - 5))} := \frac{(7 + (48 - 3))}{(2 \times (6 - (1 - 905)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{7803}{296514} & := \frac{((7-8) \times (0-3))}{(2 \times (9 + (6 \times (5 - (1-4)))))} := \frac{(7 - (8 \times (0 \times 3)))}{(2 + ((9 + (6 + 51)) \times 4))} := \frac{(7 - (8 \times (0 - 3)))}{(2 \times ((9 \times (65 \times 1)) + 4))} \\ & := \frac{(7 - (8 + (0 - 3)))}{(2 + (9 + (65 \times (1^4))))} := \frac{(7 + (8 - (0 \times 3)))}{(2 \times ((9 + 6) \times (5 + 14)))} := \frac{(7 + (8 - (0 - 3)))}{(29 + (651 + 4))} \\ & := \frac{(7 + (8 + (0 - 3)))}{(((2 \times (9 \times 6)) + (5 + 1)) \times 4)} := \frac{(78 - (0 \times 3))}{(2965 - (1^4))} := \frac{(78 - (0 - 3))}{(((2^9) \times 6) + (5 + (1^4)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{7832}{415096} & := \frac{(((7 \times 8) - 3)^2)}{((4 - (1 - 50))^{9-6})} := \frac{((7 \times 8) - (3 \times 2))}{(4 - ((1 - 50) \times (9 \times 6)))} := \frac{((7 \times 8) - (3 + 2))}{(4 - (1 - (50 \times (9 \times 6))))} \\ & := \frac{(7 - (8 - (3 \times 2)))}{((4 + 1) \times (50 + (9 - 6)))} := \frac{(7 - (8 - (3 + 2)))}{(4 \times (1 \times (50 + (9 - 6))))} := \frac{(7 + (8 - (3^2)))}{(((41 - (5 - 0)) \times 9) - 6)} \\ & := \frac{(7 + (8 \times (3 - 2)))}{((4 - (1 - 50)) \times (9 + 6))} := \frac{(78 - (3 \times 2))}{(4 \times ((150 + 9) \times 6))} := \frac{(78 - (3 - 2))}{((4 \times (1 + (5 - 0))) - (9 + 6))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{7836}{215490} & := \frac{((7 \times 8) - 36)}{(2 - (1 - (549 - 0)))} := \frac{((7 + (8 - 3)) \times 6)}{((2 + (1 \times (5 \times 4))) \times 90)} := \frac{(7 - (8 - (3 + 6)))}{(2 \times (1 \times ((5 \times 4) + 90)))} \\ & := \frac{(7 - (8 + (3 - 6)))}{(2 - (1 - (5 + (49 - 0))))} := \frac{(7 \times (8 \times (3 \times 6)))}{(2 \times (154 \times 90))} := \frac{(7 + (8 - (3 + 6)))}{(2 + (154 + (9 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{(7 + (8 - (3 - 6)))}{((2 - (1 - 54)) \times (9 - 0))} := \frac{(7 + (8 + (3 - 6)))}{((21 \times (5 \times 4)) - 90)} := \frac{(7 + (83 - 6))}{(21 \times ((5 \times 4) + 90))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{7902}{458316} & := \frac{((7 + (9 - 0)) \times 2)}{(4 \times ((5 + (8 \times 3)) \times 16))} := \frac{((7 + (9 - 0))^2)}{(4 \times (58 \times ((3 - 1)^6)))} := \frac{((7 - 9) \times (0 - 2))}{(4 \times (((5 + 8) \times (3 + 1)) + 6))} \\ & := \frac{(7 + (9 - (0 \times 2)))}{(4 \times (58 \times (3 + (1^6))))} := \frac{(7 + (9 - (0 - 2)))}{(((4^5) + (8 + ((3 - 1) \times 6)))} := \frac{(7 + (9^{02}))}{(((4^5) \times (8 - 3)) - 16)} \\ & := \frac{(7 + (9 + (0 - 2)))}{(4 \times ((5 + (8 \times 3)) \times (1 + 6)))} := \frac{(7 + 902)}{(((4 \times ((5 + 8)^3)) - 1) \times 6)} := \frac{(79 - (0 \times 2))}{(4583 - (1^6))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8496}{132750} & := \frac{((8 \times 4) + 96)}{((1 + (32 + 7)) \times 50)} := \frac{((8 - 4) \times 96)}{((1 + 3) \times (2 \times 750))} := \frac{(8 \times ((4 \times 9) + 6))}{((1 + (3 \times 2)) \times 750)} \\ & := \frac{(8 \times ((4 \times 9) - 6))}{(1 \times ((3 + 2) \times 750))} := \frac{(8 \times (4 \times (9 + 6)))}{((1 + (3^2)) \times 750)} := \frac{(8 \times (4 \times (9 - 6)))}{(1 \times ((3 + 27) \times 50))} \\ & := \frac{(8^{4-9+6})}{((1 - (3 - 27)) \times (5 - 0))} := \frac{(8 + (4 \times (9 \times 6)))}{((1 + (3^2)) \times (7 \times 50))} := \frac{(8 + (4^{9-6}))}{((1 + (32 \times 7)) \times (5 - 0))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8769}{254301} & := \frac{(((8 - 7)^6)^9)}{((2 - (5 - 4)) \times (30 - 1))} := \frac{((8 \times 7) - (6 \times 9))}{((2 - (5 \times (4 \times 3))) \times (0 - 1))} := \frac{((8 \times 7) + (6 - 9))}{(((2^{5+4}) \times (3 - 0)) + 1)} \\ & := \frac{(8 - (7 \times (6 - 9)))}{((25 + 4)^{3-01})} := \frac{(8 - (7 + (6 - 9)))}{(2 - (5 - ((4 \times 30) - 1)))} := \frac{(8 \times (7 + (6 - 9)))}{(2 + ((5^4) + 301))} \\ & := \frac{(8 + ((7 \times 6) - 9))}{((2 \times ((5^4) - 30)) - 1)} := \frac{(8 + (7 - (6 - 9)))}{(2 \times (5 + (4^{3+01})))} := \frac{(8 + (7 + (6 + 9)))}{(2 \times (5 + (430 \times 1)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9018}{267534} & := \frac{(9 - (0 - (1 + 8)))}{(2 + ((67 \times (5 + 3)) - 4))} := \frac{(9 - (0 \times 18))}{((2^6) - (7 \times (5 - 34)))} := \frac{(9 - (0 - 18))}{(267 + 534)} \\ & := \frac{(9 \times (0 - (1 - 8)))}{((26 \times 75) - (3^4))} := \frac{(9 \times (0 + (1 \times 8)))}{(267 \times ((5 - 3) \times 4))} := \frac{(9 \times (0 + (1 + 8)))}{(2 + ((6 - (7 - (5 + 3)))^4))} \\ & := \frac{(90 \times (1^8))}{(((2 \times 6) - 7) \times 534)} := \frac{(90 + (1 + 8))}{(267 \times ((5 \times 3) - 4))} := \frac{(90 + 18)}{(267 \times (5 + (3 + 4)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9018}{273546} &:= \frac{(9 - (0 - (1 + 8)))}{((2 \times (7 + (3^5))) + 46)} := \frac{(9 - (0 \times 18))}{(273 \times (5 - 4)^6)} := \frac{(9 - (0 - 18))}{(273 \times (5 + (4 - 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 \times (0 - (1 - 8)))}{(273 \times (5 - (4 - 6)))} := \frac{(9 \times (0 + (1 \times 8)))}{(2 \times (7 \times ((3 \times 54) - 6))} := \frac{(9 \times (0 + (1 + 8)))}{(27 + ((3^5) \times (4 + 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(9^{-01+8})}{(273 \times ((5 + 4)^6))} := \frac{(90 \times (1^8))}{(((2 \times (7^3)) - 5) \times 4) + 6)} := \frac{(90 + 18)}{(2 \times (7 \times ((35 + 4) \times 6)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9165}{348270} &:= \frac{((9 - (1 - 6)) \times 5)}{(((3 \times (4 + 8)) + 2) \times 70)} := \frac{((9 \times (1 + 6)) + 5)}{(34 \times (8 - (2 - 70)))} := \frac{(9 - ((1^6) \times 5))}{((3^4) + ((8^2) + (7 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 - ((1^6) + 5))}{(34 + (8 + (2 + 70)))} := \frac{(9 - (1 + (6 - 5)))}{(3 + ((4 \times (8^2)) + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(9 \times (1 + (6 - 5)))}{(3 \times (4 \times ((8^2) - (7 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 + ((1^6) \times 5))}{((3 + 4) \times (8 - (2 - 70)))} := \frac{(9 + ((1^6) - 5))}{((3 \times (4 \times (8 + 2))) + 70)} := \frac{(9 + (1 + (6 + 5)))}{(3 \times (4 - (8 - 270)))} \end{aligned}$$

3.9 10 Equivalent Blocks

• Five Digit's Numerator

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10736}{25498} &:= \frac{10 + (7 - (3 + 6))}{2 - ((5 \times (4 - 9)) + 8)} := \frac{1 \times ((07 + (3 + 6)))}{2 - (5 - (49 - 8))} := \frac{1 \times (((07 - 3) \times 6))}{2 + (54 + (9 - 8))} := \frac{10 \times ((7 + 3) \times 6)}{25 \times (49 + 8)} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (7 \times (3 + 6)))}{((2^5) - (4 + 9)) \times 8} := \frac{1 - (0 - (73 + 6))}{2 + ((5 \times (4 \times 9)) + 8)} := \frac{(10 + (7 + 3)) \times 6}{2 - (5 - (4 \times (9 \times 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - 7)) \times (3 \times 6)}{2 + (5 \times (4 \times (9 + 8)))} := \frac{(10 \times (7 \times 3)) + 6}{(2^5+4) + (9 - 8)} := \frac{10 \times ((7 - 3) \times 6)}{2 \times (5 \times (49 + 8))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{12396}{80574} &:= \frac{1 \times (2 + (3 + (9 - 6)))}{(8 \times ((0 \times 5) + 7)) - 4} := \frac{1 + ((2 \times 3) + (9 - 6))}{80 - (5 \times (7 - 4))} := \frac{1 \times (2 \times (3 + (9 - 6)))}{80 - (5 - (7 - 4))} := \frac{1 + ((2 \times 3) + (9 + 6))}{(8 - (0 - 5)) \times (7 + 4)} \\ &:= \frac{1 + (((2 + 3) \times 9) - 6)}{(8 - (0 - 57)) \times 4} := \frac{1 + (2 + (3 \times (9 + 6)))}{8 \times (((05 \times 7) + 4))} := \frac{1 - (2 - (3 + (9 \times 6)))}{(8 - (0 - 5)) \times (7 \times 4)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((2^3) + (9 \times 6))}{(80 \times 5) + (7 - 4)} := \frac{(1^{239}) \times 6}{8 - (0 - ((5 \times 7) - 4))} := \frac{1 \times ((2 + 3) \times 96)}{80 \times ((5 \times 7) + 4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{17496}{32805} &:= \frac{1 + (7^{4-9+6})}{3 \times (2 + (8 + (0 - 5)))} := \frac{1 - (7 + ((4 - 9) \times 6))}{3 \times (2 + (8 - (0 - 5)))} := \frac{1 \times ((7 + (4 - 9))^6)}{(32 - (8 - 0)) \times 5} := \frac{1 \times (74 + (9 \times 6))}{3 \times (2 \times (8 \times (05)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 7) \times ((4 \times 9) - 6)}{3 \times (2 \times (80 - 5))} := \frac{(1 + (7 + (4 \times 9))) \times 6}{3 \times ((2 \times 80) + 5)} := \frac{(1 + 7) \times (49 + 6)}{3 \times (280 - 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(1^{74}) + (9 + 6)}{3 \times (2 + (8 - (0 \times 5)))} := \frac{(1 - (7 \times (4 - 9))) \times 6}{3 + (2 + (80 \times 5))} := \frac{1 + (7 + (4 \times (9 \times 6)))}{3 \times (28 \times (05))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{18936}{52074} &:= \frac{1 + ((8 - 9) \times (3 - 6))}{5 - (2 \times (0 - (7 - 4)))} := \frac{1 \times (8 - (9 - (3 + 6)))}{5 + (20 - (7 - 4))} := \frac{1 \times ((8 - (9 - 3)) \times 6)}{(5 - (2 - 0)) \times (7 + 4)} := \frac{1 - (8 + (9 - 36))}{52 - (0 - (7 - 4))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - ((8 - 9) \times 3)) \times 6}{(5 \times (2 \times (07))) - 4} := \frac{(1^8) - (9 - 36)}{5 - (2 + (0 - 74))} := \frac{1 + (8 - (9 - 36))}{5 + (20 + 74)} \\ &:= \frac{(1^8) + (93 + 6)}{(5 + 20) \times (7 + 4)} := \frac{1 \times (8 \times (9 + (3 \times 6)))}{520 + 74} := \frac{18 + (9 + (3^6))}{5 + 2074} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19560}{74328} &:= \frac{1 \times (9 + (5 + (6 - 0)))}{74 - ((3 \times 2) - 8)} := \frac{1 + ((9 - 5) \times (6 - 0))}{7 + (4 + (3 \times 28))} := \frac{1 + (95 - (6 - 0))}{(7 - (4^3)) \times (2 - 8)} := \frac{(1 + (9 - 5)) \times (6 - 0)}{74 + (32 + 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + (9 + (5 \times (6 - 0)))}{((7 \times 4) - (3^2)) \times 8} := \frac{(1^{95}) \times 60}{(74 \times 3) - (2 - 8)} := \frac{1 + (9 + (5 + 60))}{(7 \times 43) - (2 \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + ((9 + 5) \times (6 - 0))}{(7 \times (43 + 2)) + 8} := \frac{1 \times ((9 \times 5) + 60)}{7 \times (((4 + 3)^2) + 8)} := \frac{195 + 60}{(((7 \times 4) + 3)^2) + 8} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20167}{83549} &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 \times 16)) + 7}{8 + (3 + (5 + (4 + 9)))} := \frac{2 + (0 - (1 - (6 + 7)))}{83 + (5 \times (4 - 9))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (1^6))) \times 7}{(8 \times (3 + (5 + 4))) - 9} := \frac{2 \times ((01 + (6 + 7)))}{8 + ((3 + (5 + 4)) \times 9)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (0 - (1 - 6))) \times 7}{8 + (3 \times (5 \times (4 + 9)))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (1 + 6))) \times 7}{(83 - 54) \times 9} := \frac{(20 - (1 + 6)) \times 7}{((8 \times 3) + 5) \times (4 + 9)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - 16)) \times 7}{(8^3) + (5 - (4 - 9))} := \frac{(20 + 16) \times 7}{((8 \times (3 \times 5)) - 4) \times 9} := \frac{(2^{01 \times 6}) \times 7}{8 + (3 \times ((5^4) - 9))} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23175}{64890} &:= \frac{2 - ((3 \times (1 - 7)) + 5)}{6 - ((4 - 8) \times (9 - 0))} := \frac{2 \times (3 + (1 \times (7 + 5)))}{6 - (4 + (8 - 90))} := \frac{(2 \times (3 + 17)) + 5}{6 \times (4 + (8 + (9 - 0)))} := \frac{((2^3) - (1 - 7)) \times 5}{(6 - 4) \times (8 + 90)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + (((3 - 1)^7) + 5)}{(6 \times 48) + 90} := \frac{(23 - (1 - 7)) \times 5}{(6^4) - 890} := \frac{2 + (3 + 175)}{(64 - 8) \times (9 - 0)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2^3 \times 1) \times (7 \times 5)}{64 + (8 \times 90)} := \frac{(23 + 1) \times (7 \times 5)}{6 \times (4 \times (8 + 90))} := \frac{(23 + 1) \times 75}{(64 - 8) \times 90} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23571}{68094} &:= \frac{(2 \times (3 - (5 - 7))) - 1}{(6 - 8) \times (0 - (9 + 4))} := \frac{2 + (3 + (5 + (7 + 1)))}{(6 \times (8 - (0 \times 9))) + 4} := \frac{((2 - (3 - 5)) \times 7) - 1}{6 \times (8 - (0 - (9 - 4)))} := \frac{(2 \times (3 \times 5)) + (7 - 1)}{68 - (0 - (9 \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + (3 + (5 \times (7 + 1)))}{((6 + (8 - 0)) \times 9) + 4} := \frac{2 \times (35 - (7 + 1))}{((6 \times (8 - 0)) - 9) \times 4} := \frac{2 + ((3 \times (5 \times 7)) + 1)}{(6 - (8 \times (0 - 9))) \times 4} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (3 \times ((5 \times 7) + 1))}{6 \times (8 \times ((09 + 4)))} := \frac{2 + (3 + (57 + 1))}{(6 + (8 - 0)) \times (9 + 4)} := \frac{235 + 71}{68 \times ((09 + 4))} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25697}{40381} &:= \frac{25 - (6 - (9 - 7))}{(4 \times ((0 \times 3) + 8)) + 1} := \frac{2 + (5 - ((6 - 9) \times 7))}{4 \times ((03 + (8 \times 1)))} := \frac{2 - ((5 \times 6) - (9 \times 7))}{((4 - (0 - 3)) \times 8) - 1} := \frac{(2 \times 56) - (9 \times 7)}{40 + (38 - 1)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + (56 - (9 - 7))}{4 - (0 - (3 + 81))} := \frac{(2 - (5 - 6)) \times (9 \times 7)}{((40 - 3) \times 8) + 1} := \frac{2 - (5 + (6 - (9 + 7)))}{4 - ((0 \times 3) - (8 - 1))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^5) - (6 - 9)) \times 7}{4 - (0 - 381)} := \frac{(2 + 5) \times (6^{9-7})}{403 - (8 - 1)} := \frac{2 \times ((5 + (6 + 9)) \times 7)}{40 \times (3 + (8 \times 1))} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25930}{67418} &:= \frac{(2^5) - (9 \times (3 - 0))}{6 - (7 + (4 - 18))} := \frac{(2^5) - (9 + (3 - 0))}{(6 \times (7 + (4 - 1))) - 8} := \frac{(2 \times (5 + 9)) - (3 - 0)}{(6 \times (7 + 4)) - (1^8)} := \frac{2 \times ((5 \times 9) - 30)}{6 \times ((7 \times (4 - 1)) - 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (5 \times (9 - (3 - 0)))}{(6 + 7) \times (4 + (1 \times 8))} := \frac{2 - (5 - (93 - 0))}{6 \times (7 + (4 \times (1 \times 8)))} := \frac{2 + (5 + (93 - 0))}{(67 \times (4 \times 1)) - 8} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (5 \times (9 + (3 - 0)))}{(6 + 7) \times ((4 - 1) \times 8)} := \frac{2 \times ((5 \times 9) + 30)}{6 + ((7 + 41) \times 8)} := \frac{(2 - (5 - 9)) \times 30}{(6 + 7) \times (4 \times (1 + 8))} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{27459}{81360} &:= \frac{2 + (7 + (4 + (5 + 9)))}{8 \times (1 + (3 + (6 - 0)))} := \frac{(2 - (7 \times (4 - 5))) \times 9}{(8 - (1 + 3)) \times 60} := \frac{(2 + (7 + (4 + 5))) \times 9}{8 \times ((1^3) \times 60)} := \frac{((2 \times (7 + 4)) + 5) \times 9}{(8 + (1 + 3)) \times 60} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^7) + (4^5)) \times 9}{(8 \times (1 \times 3)) \times 60} := \frac{2 \times (7 + (4 \times 59))}{8 \times (1 \times (3 \times 60))} := \frac{(2 + 7) \times ((4^5) \times 9)}{(8 \times (1 + 3)) \times 60} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times ((7 \times 45) + 9)}{8 \times ((1 + 3) \times 60)} := \frac{27 \times (45 - 9)}{8 \times (1 \times 360)} := \frac{27 \times (4 + 59)}{(81 + 3) \times 60}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{27918}{30456} & := \frac{2 - (7 - (9 - (1 - 8)))}{3 \times (0 - (4 \times (5 - 6)))} := \frac{2 - (7 - (9 + 18))}{(3 + (0 - (4 - 5))) \times 6} := \frac{(2 \times (7 + 9)) + (1^8)}{30 - ((4 - 5) \times 6)} := \frac{27 + (9 + (1 \times 8))}{(3 - ((0 \times 4) - 5)) \times 6} \\ & := \frac{2 + ((7 \times (9 - 1)) + 8)}{(3 - (0 - (4 + 5))) \times 6} := \frac{(2 \times 7) - (9 \times (1 - 8))}{30 + ((4 + 5) \times 6)} := \frac{2 + (7 \times (9 + (1 \times 8)))}{3 \times ((04 \times (5 + 6)))} \\ & := \frac{(27 \times 9) - (1^8)}{(30 \times (4 + 5)) - 6} := \frac{(2 \times 79) - (1 - 8)}{3 \times ((04 + 56))} := \frac{((2 \times (7 + 9)) + 1) \times 8}{(3 - (0 - 45)) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{27945}{68310} & := \frac{2 + (7 - (9 - (4 + 5)))}{6 + (8 \times (3 - (1 - 0)))} := \frac{2 + (7 + (9 + (4 + 5)))}{6 \times (8 + (3 \times (1 - 0)))} := \frac{2 \times (7 - (9 - (4 \times 5)))}{6 + (83 - (1 - 0))} := \frac{2 + (7 - (9 - 45))}{6 + (8 \times (3 + 10))} \\ & := \frac{2 + (7 + (9 + 45))}{(6 \times (8 \times 3)) + 10} := \frac{2 + (7 - (9 \times (4 - 5)))}{6 + (8 + (3 \times 10))} := \frac{2 + (79 + 45)}{6 - (8 - 310)} \\ & := \frac{2 \times ((7 \times 9) + 45)}{6 + ((8^3) + 10)} := \frac{27 \times (9 - (4 - 5))}{6 \times ((8 + 3) \times 10)} := \frac{(2 + 7) \times ((9 \times 4) - 5)}{683 - (1 - 0)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{29364}{80751} & := \frac{2^{9+3-6-4}}{8 - (0 - (7 - (5 - 1)))} := \frac{2 \times (9 - (3 + (6 - 4)))}{80 - (7 + 51)} := \frac{2 + (9 + (3 + (6 + 4)))}{8 - (0 - (7 + 51))} := \frac{2 \times (9 + (3 + (6 - 4)))}{80 - (7 - (5 - 1))} \\ & := \frac{2 \times (9 - (3 - (6 + 4)))}{8 \times ((07 + (5 - 1)))} := \frac{2 + (9 \times (3 \times (6 - 4)))}{80 + (75 - 1)} := \frac{(2 \times (9 \times (3 \times 6))) - 4}{80 \times (7 + (5 - 1))} \\ & := \frac{2 \times (9 - (3 - (6 - 4)))}{8 - (0 - ((7 \times 5) + 1))} := \frac{2 + (9 \times ((3 \times 6) - 4))}{8 \times (0 - (7 - 51))} := \frac{(2^9) + 364}{8 - (0 - (7^{5-1}))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{29385}{76401} & := \frac{2 - (9 - (3^{8-5}))}{7 + (6 + (40 - 1))} := \frac{(2 \times (9 - 3)) + (8 + 5)}{(7 + 6) \times (4 - (0 - 1))} := \frac{(2 \times (9 + (3 + 8))) + 5}{76 + (40 + 1)} := \frac{(2 \times ((9 \times 3) + 8)) - 5}{(7 \times (6 \times (4 - 0))) + 1} \\ & := \frac{(2 + (9 + (3 \times 8))) \times 5}{7 \times (64 - (0 - 1))} := \frac{((2 \times 9) - 3) \times (8 + 5)}{(7 + 6) \times (40 - 1)} := \frac{2 \times ((9 + (3 + 8)) \times 5)}{(7 + 6) \times (40 \times 1)} \\ & := \frac{((2 + 9) \times 3) + 8 \times 5}{(7 + 6) \times (40 + 1)} := \frac{(2 \times (9 - 3)) + (8 - 5)}{(7 - 6) \times (40 - 1)} := \frac{2 + (9 - (3 + (8 - 5)))}{7 + (6 - (4 \times (0 \times 1)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{30481}{69275} & := \frac{3 \times ((04 + (8 - 1)))}{6 + ((9^2) - (7 + 5))} := \frac{30 + (4 \times (8 + 1))}{6 + (9 + (27 \times 5))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 - (4 - 8))) - 1}{6 + (9 - (2 - (7 + 5)))} := \frac{30 + (48 - 1)}{((6 \times (9 - 2)) - 7) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{3 - (0 - (4 + 81))}{((6 \times 9) - (2 \times 7)) \times 5} := \frac{3 \times ((04 \times 8) + 1)}{((6 \times 9) - (2 + 7)) \times 5} := \frac{3 \times (0 - (4 - 81))}{(6 + (92 + 7)) \times 5} \\ & := \frac{304 - (8 - 1)}{(6 + 9) \times ((2 + 7) \times 5)} := \frac{30 \times (4 + (8 - 1))}{6 \times (((9 \times 2) + 7) \times 5)} := \frac{30 \times ((4 \times 8) + 1)}{(6 + 9) \times (2 \times 75)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{31824}{59670} & := \frac{3 - (1 - (8 + (2 - 4)))}{5 + (9 - (6 - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 - (1 - (8 - 2))) \times 4}{5 - (9 + (6 - 70))} := \frac{3 \times (1 \times (8 + (2 \times 4)))}{5 + (9 + (6 + 70))} := \frac{(3 + (1 + (8 + 2))) \times 4}{5 \times ((9 - 6) \times (7 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{3 \times (1 \times (8 + (2^4)))}{59 + (6 + 70)} := \frac{(3 \times (18 \times 2)) - 4}{(5^{9-6}) + 70} := \frac{(3 - 1) \times ((8^2) + 4)}{5 \times (9 + (6 \times (7 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{((3 - 1)^8) - (2 \times 4)}{(5 \times 9) + (6 \times 70)} := \frac{((3 - 1)^8) + 24}{5 \times ((9 + 6) \times (7 - 0))} := \frac{318 - (2 + 4)}{5 \times (9 \times (6 + (7 - 0)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{35469}{81072} & := \frac{(3 \times 5) - (4 + (6 - 9))}{(8 + (1 - (0 - 7))) \times 2} := \frac{((3 - (5 - 4)) \times 6) + 9}{8 \times (1 - (0 - (7 - 2)))} := \frac{35 - (4 - (6 - 9))}{8^{107 \times 2}} := \frac{3 - (5 - (46 - 9))}{8 - (1 \times (0 - 72))} \\ & := \frac{3 + (5 - (4 + (6 - 9)))}{8 - (1 + (0 - (7 + 2)))} := \frac{3 - (5 - (4 + (6 \times 9)))}{8 \times ((1 - (0 - 7)) \times 2)} := \frac{3 + ((5 \times 4) + (6 \times 9))}{(81 - (0 - 7)) \times 2} \\ & := \frac{3 + (5 + (4 \times (6 \times 9)))}{8 \times ((1 - (0 - 7))^2)} := \frac{(3 + (54 + 6)) \times 9}{(8 + 10) \times 72} := \frac{(3 + 5) \times 469}{8 \times 1072} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{37926}{54180} &:= \frac{(3 - (7 - (9 + 2))) \times 6}{5 \times (4 + (1 \times (8 - 0)))} := \frac{3 + (7 + (9 - (2 \times 6)))}{5 + (4 + (1^8 + 0))} := \frac{3 + (79 - 26)}{5 - (4 + (1 - 80))} := \frac{(3 \times 7) + ((9 - 2) \times 6)}{5 + (4 + (1 + 80))} \\
 &:= \frac{3 + (79 - (2 \times 6))}{(5 \times (4 \times 1)) + 80} := \frac{3 \times (7 + (9 + (2 \times 6)))}{5 \times ((4 - 1) \times (8 - 0))} := \frac{(3 \times (7 + 9)) + (2^6)}{5 \times (4 \times (1 \times (8 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times (7 + (9 + 26))}{5 \times (4 \times (1 + (8 - 0)))} := \frac{3 \times ((7 + (9 - 2)) \times 6)}{5 \times (4 \times (18 - 0))} := \frac{3 \times (7 \times ((9 \times 2) + 6))}{(5 + (4 \times 1)) \times 80} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41706}{95328} &:= \frac{4 + (17 - (0 \times 6))}{((9 - 5^3) - (2 \times 8))} := \frac{4 \times (1 \times (7 - (0 \times 6)))}{(9 + (5 - (3 \times 2))) \times 8} := \frac{(4 + 1) \times (7 - (0 \times 6))}{(9 - (5 - (3 \times 2))) \times 8} := \frac{41 + (7 + (0 - 6))}{95 + ((3^2) - 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (1 + (7 - (0 - 6)))}{9 + ((5^3) + (2 - 8))} := \frac{41 + (70 - 6)}{(9 + (5 \times 3)) \times (2 + 8)} := \frac{(4 + (17 - 0)) \times 6}{(9 - (5 - 32)) \times 8} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (1 \times (7 \times (06)))}{(9 + (5 \times 3)) \times (2 \times 8)} := \frac{(4 \times 170) + 6}{(95 + 3) \times (2 \times 8)} := \frac{(4 + 1) \times (7 \times (06))}{(9 + (53 - 2)) \times 8} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{45096}{73281} &:= \frac{4 \times (5 + (0 - (9 - 6)))}{7 - (3 - (2 + (8 - 1)))} := \frac{4^{5-09+6}}{7 + (3 + (2 \times (8 \times 1)))} := \frac{4 + (5 - (0 - (9 + 6)))}{7 + (3 + (28 + 1))} := \frac{4 \times (5 - (0 - (9 - 6)))}{7 + (3 \times ((2 \times 8) - 1))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (5 + (0 - 9))) \times 6}{7 + (((3^2) \times 8) - 1)} := \frac{(4^5 + 0) + 96}{7 \times (3 + ((2^8) + 1))} := \frac{4 + ((5 - (0 - 9)) \times 6)}{(7 \times 32) - 81} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - 5) \times (0 - 96)}{73 + (2 + 81)} := \frac{(45 + (0 - 9)) \times 6}{(7 + 32) \times (8 + 1)} := \frac{(4 \times 50) - 96}{(7 \times (32 - 8)) + 1} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{45360}{89712} &:= \frac{4 + (536 - 0)}{89 \times ((7 - 1) \times 2)} := \frac{45 \times (36 - 0)}{89 \times ((7 - 1)^2)} := \frac{(4 + 5) \times 360}{8 + ((9 + 71)^2)} := \frac{4 \times (5 \times (3 + (6 - 0)))}{89 \times (7 - (1 + 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (5 \times (36 - 0))}{89 \times ((7 + 1) \times 2)} := \frac{45 + (3 \times 60)}{89 \times (7 - (1 \times 2))} := \frac{4 + (5 + (36 - 0))}{8 + (9 \times (7 + (1 \times 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(45 + 3) \times 60}{89 \times ((7 + 1)^2)} := \frac{4 \times (5 \times (3 \times (6 - 0)))}{89 \times (7 + (1^2))} := \frac{45 \times (3 + (6 - 0))}{89 \times (7 + (1 \times 2))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{45906}{72138} &:= \frac{4 - (5 - (9 - (0 - 6)))}{(7 \times (2 \times (1^3))) + 8} := \frac{(4 \times 5) + (9 - (0 - 6))}{7 + (2 \times (1 \times (3 \times 8)))} := \frac{45 - (9 + (0 - 6))}{7 + (21 + 38)} := \frac{4 + (5 \times (9 - (0 \times 6)))}{7 \times (2 + ((1^3) + 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{4 + (5 - (9 \times (0 - 6)))}{(7 + (2 \times 1)) \times (3 + 8)} := \frac{(4^5) + (90 + 6)}{(7 + 213) \times 8} := \frac{4 + (5 + (90 + 6))}{((7 \times 2) + 1) \times (3 + 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (5 + (9 - (0 \times 6)))}{(7 + (2 - (1 - 3))) \times 8} := \frac{4 - ((5 - (9 - 0)) \times 6)}{7 - (2 - (1 + 38))} := \frac{4 \times ((5 + (9 - 0)) \times 6)}{((7^2) - 1) \times (3 + 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{48792}{51360} &:= \frac{4 - (8 - ((7 \times 9) - 2))}{(5 - (1 + 3)) \times 60} := \frac{4 \times (8 - (7 - (9 \times 2)))}{(5 \times (1 + 3)) + 60} := \frac{4 - ((8 - (7 \times 9)) \times 2)}{5 \times ((1 + 3) \times (6 - 0))} := \frac{(4 \times (8 - (7 - 9))) - 2}{5 - (1 - (36 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + 7)) \times (9 \times 2)}{(5 + (1^3)) \times 60} := \frac{((4 + (8 + 7)) \times 9)^2}{513 \times 60} := \frac{4 - (8 \times (7 - 92))}{(5 - 1) \times (3 \times 60)} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times (8 + (7 \times (9 - 2)))}{(5 - (1^3)) \times 60} := \frac{4 + (8 \times ((7 + 9)^2))}{(5 + 1) \times 360} := \frac{4 \times (87 - (9 + 2))}{5 \times (1 + (3 + 60))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{68013}{92745} &:= \frac{6 - (8 + (0 - 13))}{9 - (2 - (7 - (4 - 5)))} := \frac{6 + ((8 - (0 - 1)) \times 3)}{9 - (2 + (7 - 45))} := \frac{(6 \times (8 - 0)) - (1 + 3)}{9 + ((2 \times (7 \times 4)) - 5)} := \frac{68 + (0 - 13)}{(9 + (2 \times (7 - 4))) \times 5} \\
 &:= \frac{6 \times (8 - (0 - (1 \times 3)))}{9 \times (2 + (7 - (4 - 5)))} := \frac{6 + (80 + 13)}{9 + (2 \times (7 \times (4 + 5)))} := \frac{6 - (8 \times (0 - 13))}{(9^2) + (74 - 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{6 + (8 \times (0 - (1 - 3)))}{9 - (2 - ((7 \times 4) - 5))} := \frac{6 + 8013}{9 \times (27 \times 45)} := \frac{6 \times (80 - (1 \times 3))}{(9 - (2 - 7)) \times 45}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{75438}{96012} &:= \frac{7 - (5 - (4 - (3 - 8)))}{9 + (6 + (0 - (1^2)))} := \frac{7 - (5 + (4 \times (3 - 8)))}{(9 + (6 + (0 - 1))) \times 2} := \frac{7 - (5 - (4 + 38))}{(9 \times (6 \times 01)) + 2} := \frac{7 + ((5 + (4 - 3)) \times 8)}{9 + (60 + (1^2))} \\ &:= \frac{7 + (54 - (3 - 8))}{96 + (0 - 12)} := \frac{7 \times ((5 - 4) \times (3 + 8))}{96 - (0 - (1 \times 2))} := \frac{7 + (54 + 38)}{9 \times ((6 - (0 - 1)) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{75 + (43 - 8)}{(9 + (60 + 1)) \times 2} := \frac{7 - (5 - (4 \times 38))}{(9 + (6 + (0 - 1)))^2} := \frac{75 - (4 + 38)}{(9 \times (6 - 0)) - 12} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{76193}{82054} &:= \frac{7 + (6 \times (1^{93}))}{8 - ((2 \times (0 - 5)) + 4)} := \frac{7 + (6 + (1 + (9 + 3)))}{8 + (20 \times (5 - 4))} := \frac{7 + (6 - (1 - (9 \times 3)))}{8 - (20 - 54)} := \frac{76 + (1 - (9 + 3))}{(8 \times (2 - 0)) + 54} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + (6 \times 1)) \times (9 - 3)}{(8 \times (2 \times (05))) + 4} := \frac{76 + (1 + (9 \times 3))}{8 \times ((2 \times (05)) + 4)} := \frac{(7 + (6 \times 1)) \times (9 + 3)}{8 \times (20 + (5 - 4))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + 6) \times (19 - 3)}{8 \times ((2 - (0 - 5)) \times 4)} := \frac{(7 + 6) \times (19 + 3)}{(82 + (0 - 5)) \times 4} := \frac{(7 \times 61) + 93}{(8 + 20) \times (5 \times 4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{86310}{92475} &:= \frac{(8 + 6) \times (3 - (1 - 0))}{9 - (2 - ((4 \times 7) - 5))} := \frac{(8 + 6) \times (3 \times (1 - 0))}{9 + (24 + (7 + 5))} := \frac{86 - (3 \times 10)}{9 + ((2 \times (4 \times 7)) - 5)} := \frac{8 + (63 - (1 - 0))}{(9 - (2 \times (4 - 7))) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{86 - (3 - (1 - 0))}{9 + (2 + (4 + 75))} := \frac{(8 \times (6 - 3)) - 10}{9 - (2 - (4 \times (7 - 5)))} := \frac{8 + ((6 + 3) \times 10)}{9 + (2 \times (4 \times (7 + 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 + 6) \times (3 + 10)}{(9 + (2 + (4 \times 7))) \times 5} := \frac{(8 + 6) \times (3 \times 10)}{9 \times (2 + (4 \times (7 + 5)))} := \frac{8 \times (63 \times 10)}{9 \times (2 \times (4 \times 75))} \end{aligned}$$

• **Four Digit's Numerator**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{2619}{345708} &:= \frac{((2 \times (6 \times 1)) - 9)}{(3 \times ((4 \times (5 \times (7 - 0))) - 8))} := \frac{((2 \times (6 - 1)) - 9)}{(3 \times (45 + (7 + (0 - 8))))} := \frac{((2 \times 6) + (1 + 9))}{(3 \times ((4^5) + (7 \times (0 - 8))))} := \frac{(2 - (6 - (1 \times 9)))}{(3 \times ((4 \times (57 - 0)) - 8))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (6 - (1 + 9)))}{((34 - (5 - 70)) \times 8)} := \frac{(2 - (6 + (1 - 9)))}{((3 + ((4 + 5) \times (7 - 0))) \times 8)} := \frac{(2 \times (6 + (1^9)))}{((3 + (4 \times (57 - 0))) \times 8)} \\ &:= \frac{(2^{6-1^9})}{(3 \times ((4 \times (5 \times 70)) + 8))} := \frac{(2 + (6 - (1^9)))}{(3 \times ((4 \times (5 + 70)) + 8))} := \frac{(26 + (1 + 9))}{(3 \times ((4^5) + (70 \times 8)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{2943}{176580} &:= \frac{((2^{9-4}) \times 3)}{(1 \times ((7 + 65) \times 80))} := \frac{((2 + (9 + 4)) \times 3)}{((1 - 7) \times (6 \times (5 - 80)))} := \frac{(2 - (9 - (4 \times 3)))}{(1 \times ((76 \times 5) - 80))} := \frac{(2 \times (9 - (4 - 3)))}{((176 \times 5) + 80)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (9 + (4 + 3)))}{((1 - (7 - (6 \times 5))) \times 80)} := \frac{(2 \times (9 + 43))}{((1 + (7 \times (6 + 5))) \times 80)} := \frac{(2^{9-4-3})}{((1^7) \times (6 \times (5 \times (8 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (9 - (4 - 3)))}{(((1 + 7) \times 65) + 80)} := \frac{(2 + (9 + (4 - 3)))}{((1 + (7 + (6 - 5))) \times 80)} := \frac{(29 - (4 - 3))}{(1 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (8 - 0))))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{2967}{103845} &:= \frac{(((2 \times 9) - 6) \times 7)}{((10 - 3) \times (84 \times 5))} := \frac{((2 \times (9 - 6)) + 7)}{((10 - (3 - 84)) \times 5)} := \frac{((2 \times 9) - (6 + 7))}{(1 \times (0 + ((3 + (8 \times 4)) \times 5)))} := \frac{((2^9 - 6) - 7)}{(1 + (0 - (3 + (8 - 45))))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (9 - (6 + 7)))}{(1 \times (0 + ((38 + 4) \times 5)))} := \frac{(2 - (9 \times (6 - 7)))}{(((103 - 8) \times 4) + 5)} := \frac{(2 - (9 - 67))}{(10 \times ((38 + 4) \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times ((9 - 6) \times 7))}{(10 \times ((38 \times 4) - 5))} := \frac{(2 \times (9 \times (6 + 7)))}{(1 + (0 - (3 - (8 \times (4^5)))))} := \frac{(2 \times (9 + (6 - 7)))}{(10 \times (3 + (8 + 45)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{3024}{197568} &:= \frac{(3 - (0 \times 24))}{((19 \times 7) - (5 - 68))} := \frac{(3 \times ((0 \times 2) + 4))}{(1 \times ((97 - (5 - 6)) \times 8))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 - (2 - 4)))}{(1 - (9 - ((7 \times 56) + 8)))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (2 \times 4)))}{((197 + (5 - 6)) \times 8)} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (2^4)))}{((1^9) \times (7 \times (56 \times 8)))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (2 + 4)))}{(1 \times ((9 + 75) \times (6 + 8)))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + 24))}{((1 + 97) \times (56 - 8))} \\ &:= \frac{(30 \times (2 \times 4))}{(1 \times ((9 \times 7) + ((5^6) - 8)))} := \frac{(30 \times (2^4))}{((1 + 9) \times (7 \times (56 \times 8)))} := \frac{(30 + 24)}{((1 - 9) \times (7 \times (5 - 68)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{3672}{195840} &:= \frac{(3 \times 6) - (7 + 2)}{(1 \times ((9 - (5 - 8)) \times 40))} := \frac{(3 - (6 - (7 + 2)))}{(1 \times ((9 \times (5 \times 8)) - 40))} := \frac{(3 \times ((6 + 7) \times 2))}{((1 + (95 + 8)) \times 40)} := \frac{(3 \times (6 \times (7 - 2)))}{((1 + (9 + 5)) \times (8 \times 40))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (6 + (7 + 2)))}{((1 + 9) \times (5 \times (8 + 40)))} := \frac{(3^{6-7+2})}{((1 + (9 - 5)) \times (8 \times (4 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 + (6 \times (7 + 2)))}{(1 \times (95 \times (8 \times (4 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (6 \times 72))}{((1 + 9) \times (58 \times 40))} := \frac{(3 + (6 + (7 + 2)))}{((1 - 9) \times ((5 - 8) \times 40))} := \frac{(36 - (7 + 2))}{(1 \times (9 \times (5 \times (8 \times (4 - 0))))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{3687}{129045} &:= \frac{(3 \times 6) - (8 + 7)}{((12 + (9 - (0 \times 4))) \times 5)} := \frac{((3 \times 6) + (8 + 7))}{(1 \times ((290 \times 4) - 5))} := \frac{((3 \times 6) + (8 - 7))}{((129 - (0 - 4)) \times 5)} := \frac{((3 + (6 - 8)) \times 7)}{(1 \times (290 - 45))} \\ &:= \frac{((3 + (6 - 8))^7)}{(1 - (2 + (9 + (0 - 45))))} := \frac{(3 - (6 - (8 + 7)))}{((12 + (9 - 0)) \times (4 \times 5))} := \frac{(3 \times (6 + (8 - 7)))}{(1 - (290 - (4^5)))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (6 \times (8 - 7)))}{(1 \times ((2 - 9) \times (0 - 45)))} := \frac{(3 + (6 + (8 + 7)))}{(12 \times (90 - (4 \times 5)))} := \frac{(36 \times (8 - 7))}{((1 - 29) \times (0 - 45))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{3918}{254670} &:= \frac{((3 \times 9) - (1^8))}{((2 \times 5) + (4 \times (6 \times 70)))} := \frac{((3 \times 9) + (1^8))}{((254 + 6) \times (7 - 0))} := \frac{(3 - (9 - (1 \times 8)))}{(2 \times (5 - (4 + (6 - 70))))} := \frac{(3 - (9 - (1 + 8)))}{(((2^5) \times 4) + (67 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 - (9 + (1 - 8)))}{(2 - (5 - (4 - (6 - 70))))} := \frac{(3 \times (9 + (1 - 8)))}{(2 \times (5 \times (46 - (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(3^{9+1-8})}{(2 + ((5^4) - (6 \times (7 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (9 - (1 \times 8)))}{(2 \times (54 + (6 + 70)))} := \frac{(3 + (9 \times (1 + 8)))}{(((2^5) + 46) \times 70)} := \frac{(3 + (9 + (1 \times 8)))}{(25 \times (4 \times (6 + (7 - 0))))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{3951}{426708} &:= \frac{((3 \times 9) + (5 - 1))}{(4 - ((2 - (6 \times 70)) \times 8))} := \frac{((3 + 9) \times (5 + 1))}{((4 + 2)^{6+7-08})} := \frac{((3 + 9) \times 51)}{((4^{2+6}) + (70 \times 8))} := \frac{((3 + 9)^{5-1})}{(4 \times (2 \times (6^{7-0 \times 8})))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (9 - (5 + 1)))}{((((4 \times 2) + 6) \times 70) - 8)} := \frac{(3^{9-5+1})}{(4 \times ((2 - (6 - (7 - 0)))^8))} := \frac{(3 + (9 - (5 \times 1)))}{((4 \times (2 \times 6)) + 708)} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (9 - (5 + 1)))}{(4 - ((2^6) - 708))} := \frac{(39 - (5 - 1))}{(42 \times (6 \times (7 - (0 - 8))))} := \frac{(39 + (5 \times 1))}{(((4 + (2^6)) \times 70) - 8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4168}{370952} &:= \frac{(((4 + 1) \times 6) + 8)}{((370 \times 9) + 52)} := \frac{(((4 + 1) \times 6) - 8)}{(3 - (70 - ((9 \times 5)^2)))} := \frac{((4 - (1^6)) \times 8)}{(3 \times (709 + (5 - 2)))} := \frac{((4 + (1 \times 6)) \times 8)}{((3 + 709) \times (5 \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - (1 - (6 - 8)))}{(3 - (7 + (0 - (95 - 2))))} := \frac{(4 \times (1 \times (6 + 8)))}{((3 + 709) \times (5 + 2))} := \frac{(4^{168})}{(((3 \times (70 - 9)) - 5) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (1 - (6 - 8)))}{(3 + ((70 \times 9) - (5 \times 2)))} := \frac{(4 + (1 \times (6 - 8)))}{(3 - (7 \times ((0 \times 9) - (5^2))))} := \frac{(4 + (1 + (6 - 8)))}{(3 \times (70 + (9 + (5 \times 2))))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4716}{259380} &:= \frac{((4 + 7) \times 16)}{(((2 \times 59) + 3) \times 80)} := \frac{((4 - 7) \times (1 - 6))}{(25 \times (9 + (3 \times (8 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 - (7 - (1 + 6)))}{(2 \times ((5 \times (9 - 3)) + 80))} := \frac{(4 - (7 + (1 - 6)))}{(2 \times ((5 \times (9 \times 3)) - 80))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (7 + (1^6)))}{(2 \times ((5 + (9 - 3)) \times 80))} := \frac{(4 + (7 \times (1^6)))}{((25 \times 9) + 380)} := \frac{(4 + (7 + (1 \times 6)))}{(2 - (5 - (938 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (7 + (1 + 6)))}{(2 \times (5 \times (9 \times (3 + (8 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 + (7 + (1 - 6)))}{(2 \times (5 \times (9 + (3 \times (8 - 0))))} := \frac{(47 \times (1^6))}{(2593 - (8 - 0))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4716}{398502} &:= \frac{(((4 \times 7) - 1) \times 6)}{((39 \times (8 - (5 - 0)))^2)} := \frac{((4 \times (7 - 1)) + 6)}{((3 \times 9) + (8 + (50^2)))} := \frac{((47 + 1) \times 6)}{(((3 + 9) \times (8 + (5 - 0)))^2)} := \frac{(4 \times ((7 + 1) \times 6))}{(39 \times (8 \times (50 + 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (7 - (1^6)))}{((3 + 9) \times ((8 + (5 - 0))^2))} := \frac{(4 \times (7 + (1^6)))}{((3 - (9 - (8 + 50)))^2)} := \frac{(4 \times (7 + (1 - 6)))}{(((39 - (8 + (5 - 0)))^2)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (7 + (1^6)))}{(39 \times ((8 + (5 - 0)) \times 2))} := \frac{(4 + (7 + (1 - 6)))}{(3 + (9 \times (8 \times (5 - (0 - 2))))} := \frac{(47 + (1 + 6))}{(3 \times (9 \times ((8 + (5 - 0))^2)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4826}{103759} &:= \frac{4 - (8 - (2 + 6))}{(10 \times (3 + 7)) - (5 + 9)} := \frac{(4 \times (8 - 2)) - 6}{(1 - (0 - (37 + 5))) \times 9} := \frac{4 + (8 + (2 \times 6))}{1 - (0 - (3 + ((7 - 5)^9)))} := \frac{4 - (8 \times (2 - 6))}{(((10 + 3) \times 7) - 5) \times 9} \\ &:= \frac{48 + (2 - 6)}{1 - (0 - (3 \times (7 \times (5 \times 9))))} := \frac{(4 \times (8 + 2)) + 6}{(10^3) - (7 - (5 - 9))} := \frac{(48 \times 2) - 6}{((10 \times (3 \times 7)) + 5) \times 9} \\ &:= \frac{(48 \times 2) + 6}{10 + (37 \times 59)} := \frac{4 + ((8 \times 2) + 6)}{((103 + 7) \times 5) + 9} := \frac{(4 \times 8) - 26}{103 + ((7 \times 5) - 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4739}{208516} &:= \frac{((4 \times (7 \times 3)) + 9)}{(2 - (0 - ((8^5 - 1) - 6)))} := \frac{((4 \times (7 - 3)) - 9)}{(2 - ((0 \times 8) - (51 \times 6)))} := \frac{((4 \times 7) - (3 \times 9))}{(2 \times (0 - (8 - (5 \times (1 \times 6)))))} := \frac{(4 - (7 - (3 \times 9)))}{((208 \times 5) + 16)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - (7 + (3 - 9)))}{(((2 \times (0 + 8)) + (5 + 1)) \times 6)} := \frac{(4 \times (7 - (3 - 9)))}{(208 \times (5 + (1 \times 6)))} := \frac{(4^{7+3-9})}{(2 \times (0 - (8 \times (5 - 16))))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + ((7 - 3) \times 9))}{(20 \times (8 + (5 \times 16)))} := \frac{(4 + (7 + (3 - 9)))}{((2^{0^8}) - ((5 + 1) \times 6))} := \frac{(47 - (3 \times 9))}{(20 \times (8 + ((5 + 1) \times 6)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{6345}{279180} &:= \frac{((6 + 3) \times (4 \times 5))}{(2 + (7918 - 0))} := \frac{((6 - 3) \times (4 \times 5))}{(((2 \times (7 + 9)) + 1) \times 80)} := \frac{(6 - (3 - (4 - 5)))}{(2 + (79 - (1 - (8 - 0))))} := \frac{(6 - (3 + (4 - 5)))}{(2 \times (7 + (9 \times (1 + (8 - 0)))))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times (3 + (4 - 5)))}{(((2 + ((7 \times 9) + 1)) \times (8 - 0))} := \frac{(6 \times (3 + 45))}{((2^7) \times (91 + (8 - 0)))} := \frac{(6 + ((3 - 4) \times 5))}{((2 \times ((7 \times 9) - 1)) - 80)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + (3 \times (4 - 5)))}{((2 \times (7 \times (9 + 1))) - (8 - 0))} := \frac{(6 + (3 + (4 + 5)))}{((2 + 7) \times (9 - (1 - 80)))} := \frac{(6 + (3 + 45))}{(27 \times (9 - (1 - 80)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{6354}{289107} &:= \frac{((6 - (3 - 5)) \times 4)}{(2 \times (8 \times (91 - (0 \times 7))))} := \frac{((6 \times 35) + 4)}{((2 + 89) \times 107)} := \frac{((6 + (3 \times 5)) \times 4)}{((2 - 8) \times (91 \times (0 - 7)))} := \frac{((6 + (3 + 5)) \times 4)}{(28 \times (91 - (0 \times 7)))} \\ &:= \frac{((6 + (3 - 5)) \times 4)}{((2 + 89) \times (1 - (0 - 7)))} := \frac{(6 - ((3 - 5) \times 4))}{((2 + (89 \times (1 - 0))) \times 7)} := \frac{(6 - (3 - (5 - 4)))}{(2 \times (8 + ((9 \times 10) - 7)))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - (3 + (5 - 4)))}{((2 - (8 - (9 + 10))) \times 7)} := \frac{(6 \times (3 - (5 - 4)))}{((2 - (8 \times (9 + 1))) \times (0 - 7))} := \frac{(6 + ((3 + 5) \times 4))}{(((2^8) - (9 \times (1 - 0))) \times 7)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{6984}{370152} &:= \frac{(6 - ((9 - 8) \times 4))}{(3 - ((7 \times (0 - 15)) + 2))} := \frac{(6 - ((9 - 8)^4))}{((3 \times (70 + 1)) + 52)} := \frac{(6 - (9 - (8 + 4)))}{(3 \times (7 - (0 - 152)))} := \frac{(6 - (9 - (8 - 4)))}{(((3 + (7 - (0 - 1))) \times 5) - 2)} \\ &:= \frac{(6^{(9-8)^4})}{(3 \times (70 + ((1 + 5)^2))} := \frac{(6 + ((9 - 8) \times 4))}{((3 + (7 - 0)) \times (1 + 52))} := \frac{(6 + ((9 - 8)^4))}{(370 + (1^52))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + (9 - (8 + 4)))}{(3 \times (70 - (15 + 2)))} := \frac{(69 - (8 \times 4))}{(37 \times (0 + (1 + 52)))} := \frac{(69 + (8 - 4))}{((3 + 70) \times (1 + 52))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{7398}{140562} &:= \frac{((7 \times 3) + (9 - 8))}{(1 + (405 + (6 \times 2)))} := \frac{((7 + (3 - 9)) \times 8)}{(1 \times (40 + (56 \times 2)))} := \frac{((7 + (3 - 9))^8)}{(1 - (4 + (0 - ((5 + 6) \times 2))))} := \frac{(7 - (3 - (9 - 8)))}{(1 + (40 + (56 - 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 - (3 \times (9 - 8)))}{(((14 - (0 - 5)) \times (6 - 2))} := \frac{(7 - (3 + (9 - 8)))}{(1 - (4 + (0 - (5 \times (6 \times 2)))))} := \frac{(7 + ((3 \times 9) + 8))}{(1 \times ((405 - 6) \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + (3 - (9 - 8)))}{((1 - (4 - 0)) \times (5 - 62))} := \frac{(7 + (3 + (9 - 8)))}{(1 + (((40 - 5) \times 6) - 2))} := \frac{(73 + 98)}{(((1^4 + 0) + 56)^2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{7956}{143208} &:= \frac{((7 \times 9) - (5 - 6))}{(1 \times (((4 \times 3)^2 + 0) \times 8))} := \frac{((7 \times 9) - 56)}{(14 \times (3 - (2 + (0 - 8))))} := \frac{((7 - 9) \times (5 - 6))}{(1 \times (4 \times (3 - (2 + (0 - 8)))))} := \frac{(7 - (9 - (5 \times 6)))}{(1 \times ((43 + 20) \times 8))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 - (9 - (5 + 6)))}{(1 + (4 - (3 - (20 \times 8))))} := \frac{(7 - (9 \times (5 - 6)))}{(1 \times (4 \times ((3^2 + 0) \times 8)))} := \frac{(7 \times (9 + (5 - 6)))}{((1 - (4^3)) \times (2 \times (0 - 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + (9 + (5 - 6)))}{(14 - (32 \times (0 - 8)))} := \frac{(7 + (95 + 6))}{(((1 + 43)^2 + 0) + 8)} := \frac{(79 - (5 - 6))}{(1432 - (0 - 8))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8037}{425961} &:= \frac{((8 \times (0 \times 3)) + 7)}{((4 \times (2 - (5 - 96))) - 1)} := \frac{(8 - (0 - (3 \times 7)))}{((4 + 25) \times ((9 \times 6) - 1))} := \frac{(8 - (0 - (3 + 7)))}{(4 + (2 \times (5 \times (96 - 1))))} := \frac{(8 - (0 - (3 - 7)))}{(4 \times ((2 \times (5 - 9)) + 61))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 - (0 \times 37))}{(4 \times (2 \times (59 - (6 \times 1))))} := \frac{(8 \times (0 - (3 - 7)))}{((4^2) \times ((5 \times 9) + 61))} := \frac{(8 \times (0 + (3 + 7)))}{((4^2) \times (5 \times ((9 \times 6) - 1)))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 + ((0 \times 3) - 7))}{(4 + (2 - (5 + (9 - 61))))} := \frac{(8 + (0 - (3 - 7)))}{((4 + 2) \times ((5 \times 9) + 61))} := \frac{(80 - (3 - 7))}{(42 \times ((5 \times 9) + 61))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8145}{276930} & := \frac{((8 - (1 + 4)) \times 5)}{(2 \times ((76 + 9) \times (3 - 0)))} := \frac{((8 + (1 \times 4)) \times 5)}{(((2 \times 7) + (6 \times 9)) \times 30)} := \frac{(8 - ((1^4) \times 5))}{(((2 \times 7) - 6) \times 9) + 30} := \frac{(8 - ((1^4) + 5))}{(2 \times (7 + (6 - (9 - 30))))} \\ & := \frac{(8 - ((1^4) - 5))}{((27 \times (6 + 9)) + (3 - 0))} := \frac{(8 - (1 - (4 - 5)))}{(2 \times ((7 \times (6 + 9)) - (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(8 - (1 \times (4 - 5)))}{(2 \times (((7 \times 6) + 9) \times (3 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{(8 - (1 + (4 - 5)))}{(2 + ((7 - 6) \times (9 \times 30)))} := \frac{(8 + (1 \times (4 + 5)))}{((2^7) + ((6 + 9) \times 30))} := \frac{(81 + (4 + 5))}{(2 \times (((7 \times 6) + 9) \times 30))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8406}{239571} & := \frac{(8 - (4 - (0 \times 6)))}{(2 + (3 + ((9 \times (5 + 7)) + 1)))} := \frac{(8 - (4 \times (0 \times 6)))}{(2 \times (3 \times ((9 \times 5) - (7 \times 1))))} := \frac{(8 - (4 + (0 - 6)))}{((2 \times ((3 \times (9 \times 5)) + 7)) + 1)} := \frac{(8 \times (4 \times (0 + 6)))}{((2^3) \times (9 \times (5 + 7)))} \\ & := \frac{(8 + (4 - (0 \times 6)))}{(((2 \times (3 \times 9)) - 5) \times 7) - 1} := \frac{(8 + (4 - (0 - 6)))}{(2 - (3 - ((9 \times 57) + 1)))} := \frac{(8 + (4 + (0 - 6)))}{(2 + (3 + (95 + 71)))} \\ & := \frac{(8 + (40 - 6))}{((23 \times (9 \times 5) + 7) + 1)} := \frac{(8 + 406)}{(23 \times (9 \times (57 \times 1)))} := \frac{(84 - (0 - 6))}{((2 + 3) \times (9 \times (57 \times 1)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8694}{352107} & := \frac{(8 - 6) \times 9 - 4}{3^{5-2+1} \times 07} := \frac{((8 \times 6) - (9 \times 4))}{((3^5) \times (2 \times (1^{07})))} := \frac{((8 \times 6) + (9 \times 4))}{((3^5) \times (2 \times (1 \times (0 + 7))))} := \frac{((8 + 6) \times (9 \times 4))}{((3^5) \times ((2 + 10) \times 7))} \\ & := \frac{((8 + 6) \times (9 + 4))}{((3 + (5 \times 210)) \times 7)} := \frac{((8 - 6) \times (9^4))}{((3^5) \times ((2 + (1 - 0))^7))} := \frac{((8 - 6) \times (9 - 4))}{(3 \times (5 \times ((2 \times 10) + 7)))} \\ & := \frac{(8 - (6 - 94))}{((3^5) \times (2 \times (1 - (0 - 7))))} := \frac{(8^{6-9+4})}{(3 + ((5 - 2) \times 107))} := \frac{(8 + (6 \times (9 - 4)))}{(3 \times ((52 \times 10) - 7))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8763}{201549} & := \frac{((8 + 7) \times (6 - 3))}{(((20 - 1) \times 54) + 9)} := \frac{((8 + 76) \times 3)}{((20 - (1 - (5^4))) \times 9)} := \frac{((8 - 7) \times (6 - 3))}{(((20^{1+5}) - (4 - 9))} := \frac{((8 - 7)^{6-3})}{(2 + (0 - (15 - (4 \times 9))))} \\ & := \frac{(8 - ((7 - 6) \times 3))}{((2 \times (0 - (1 - 54))) + 9)} := \frac{(8 - (7 - (6 + 3)))}{(((2 - (0 - 1))^5) - (4 + 9))} := \frac{(8 - (7 - (6 - 3)))}{(2 \times (0 + (1 + (54 - 9))))} \\ & := \frac{(8 + ((7 - 6)^3))}{((2 - (0 - (1 + (5 \times 4)))) \times 9)} := \frac{(8 + (7 - (6 + 3)))}{(2 \times (0 + ((15 \times 4) + 9)))} := \frac{(8 + (7 + (6 + 3)))}{(2 - (0 - (1 + 549)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9387}{206514} & := \frac{((9 + (3 + 8)) \times 7)}{(20 \times ((6 + 5) \times 14))} := \frac{((9 + (3 - 8)) \times 7)}{((2 \times (0 + (6 \times 51))) + 4)} := \frac{((93 + 8) \times 7)}{(2 \times (0 + ((6^5) + (1^4))))} := \frac{(9 - (3 - (8 + 7)))}{(206 + ((5 - 1)^4))} \\ & := \frac{(9 - (3 \times (8 - 7)))}{(2 \times (0 + (65 + (1^4))))} := \frac{(9 - (3 + (8 - 7)))}{((2 \times (0 + (6 + 51))) - 4)} := \frac{(9 \times (3 - (8 - 7)))}{(2 \times (0 - (6 - (51 \times 4))))} \\ & := \frac{(9 + (3 \times (8 - 7)))}{(2 - (0 - (6 + ((5 - 1)^4))))} := \frac{(9 + (38 - 7))}{(20 \times ((6 + (5 \times 1)) \times 4))} := \frac{(93 + (8 - 7))}{(2065 - (1 - 4))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9435}{120768} & := \frac{9 + (4 - (3 + 5))}{1 + (2 + (0 - (7 - 68)))} := \frac{9 + ((4 - 3)^5)}{1 \times (2^{-07+6+8})} := \frac{9 - (4 - (3 \times 5))}{1 \times (2^{0 \times 76+8})} := \frac{9 - 4 + 35}{1 \times 2^{07-6+8}} \\ & := \frac{9 \times ((4 - 3) \times 5)}{12 \times ((0 \times 7) + (6 \times 8))} := \frac{(9 - 4) \times (3 \times 5)}{120 \times ((7 - 6) \times 8)} := \frac{(9 + (4 \times 3)) \times 5}{(1 + (20 + 7)) \times (6 \times 8)} \\ & := \frac{((9 - 4)^3) - 5}{1 \times (2 \times (0768))} := \frac{9 \times (4 \times 35)}{(1 + 20) \times 768} := \frac{9 \times ((4 + 3) \times 5)}{12 \times ((07 \times (6 \times 8)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9732}{150846} & := \frac{(((9 - 7) \times 3) - 2)}{(((1 + (5 - (0 - 8))) \times 4) + 6)} := \frac{(((9 - 7)^3) - 2)}{(15 - (0 - (84 - 6)))} := \frac{((9 \times 7) - (3 - 2))}{(1 - (5 \times (0 - (8 \times (4 \times 6))))} := \frac{((9 + (7 - 3)) \times 2)}{(1 + ((50 \times 8) - (4 - 6)))} \\ & := \frac{((9 - 7) \times (3 \times 2))}{(((1 + (5 - 0)) \times (8 \times 4)) - 6)} := \frac{(9 - (7 - (3 \times 2)))}{(150 - ((8 \times 4) - 6))} := \frac{(9 - (7 \times (3 - 2)))}{(1 - (5 \times (0 - (8 + (4 - 6))))} \\ & := \frac{(9 + (7 - (3 \times 2)))}{(1 - ((5 \times (0 - (8 \times 4))) + 6))} := \frac{(9 + (7 + 32))}{(((15 \times (0 + 8)) + 4) \times 6)} := \frac{(9 + (73 + 2))}{(((1 + (5 - (0 \times 8)))^4) + 6)} \end{aligned}$$

3.10 11 Equivalent Blocks

• Five Digit's Numerator

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10296}{43758} &::= \frac{(1^{02}) + (9 - 6)}{4 + (3 + (7 - (5 - 8)))} ::= \frac{1 \times ((02^{9-6}))}{4 + (3 \times (7 - (5 - 8)))} ::= \frac{1 \times (((02 \times 9) - 6))}{(4 - (3 \times 7)) \times (5 - 8)} ::= \frac{(1^{02}) + (9 + 6)}{4 - (3 - (75 - 8))} \\ &::= \frac{1 \times (0 - (2 - (9 \times 6)))}{4 + ((3 \times 75) - 8)} ::= \frac{10 + ((2 + 9) \times 6)}{43 + (7 \times (5 \times 8))} ::= \frac{10 \times (2^{9-6})}{4 + ((37 + 5) \times 8)} ::= \frac{(1^{02}) \times 96}{((4^3) \times 7) - (5 \times 8)} \\ &::= \frac{(1 - (0 - 29)) \times 6}{4 + (3 + 758)} ::= \frac{10 + ((2^9) - 6)}{(437 \times 5) + 8} ::= \frac{(1 - (0 - 2)) \times 96}{((4 \times 37) + 5) \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{13470}{59268} &::= \frac{1 \times ((3 \times 4) - (7 - 0))}{(5 \times (9 \times 2)) - 68} ::= \frac{1 + (3 + (4 + (7 - 0)))}{5 - (9 - (2 + 68))} ::= \frac{1 + ((3 \times 4) + (7 - 0))}{5 + ((9^2) - (6 - 8))} ::= \frac{((1^3) + 4) \times (7 - 0)}{5 + ((9^2) + 68)} \\ &::= \frac{1 - (3 - (47 - 0))}{((5 + 9^2) - (6 - 8))} ::= \frac{1 \times (3 + (47 - 0))}{5 \times (92 - (6 \times 8))} ::= \frac{13 + (47 - 0)}{5 - (9 - 268)} ::= \frac{1 + ((3^4) - (7 - 0))}{5 \times ((9 \times 2) + (6 \times 8))} \\ &::= \frac{1 + (3 \times (4 \times (7 - 0)))}{((59 + 2) \times 6) + 8} ::= \frac{1 + (34 + 70)}{(5 \times 92) - (6 - 8)} ::= \frac{(1 - (3 - 4)) \times 70}{(5 + (9 \times (2 + 6))) \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{13794}{80256} &::= \frac{1 \times (3 - ((7 - 9) \times 4))}{8^{0+2 \times (-5+6)}} ::= \frac{((1 - 3) \times 7) + (9 \times 4)}{8 \times (((02 \times 5) + 6))} ::= \frac{1 - (3 - (7 \times (9 - 4)))}{80 + (2 \times 56)} ::= \frac{1 \times ((3 \times (7 + 9)) - 4)}{8 \times (((02 + (5 \times 6)))} \\ &::= \frac{(1 + (3 + 7)) \times (9 - 4)}{80 \times ((2 \times 5) - 6)} ::= \frac{1 + ((3 + (7 + 9)) \times 4)}{8 \times ((0 \times 2) + 56)} ::= \frac{1 - (3 \times (7 - (9 \times 4)))}{8^{02-5+6}} ::= \frac{(1 + (3 + 7)) \times (9 + 4)}{802 + (5 \times 6)} \\ &::= \frac{1 \times ((3 + (7 \times 9)) \times 4)}{8 \times (((02^5) \times 6))} ::= \frac{1 + (((3 \times 7) + 9) \times 4)}{(8^{02}) \times (5 + 6)} ::= \frac{1 + ((37 \times 9) - 4)}{(8^{02}) \times (5 \times 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{15672}{43098} &::= \frac{1 \times (5 - (6 - (7 - 2)))}{(4 \times (3 - 0)) - (9 - 8)} ::= \frac{1 \times (5 - (6 - (7 + 2)))}{(4 \times 30) - 98} ::= \frac{1 \times ((5 - (6 - 7)) \times 2)}{4 + (30 - (9 - 8))} ::= \frac{1 \times (5 + (6 + (7 - 2)))}{4 \times (3 - ((0 \times 9) - 8))} \\ &::= \frac{1 \times (5 + (6 + (7 + 2)))}{4 - (3 \times (0 - (9 + 8)))} ::= \frac{1 + (5 + (6 \times (7 - 2)))}{4 - (3 + (0 - 98))} ::= \frac{1 - (5 - ((6 \times 7) + 2))}{(4 \times (3 - 0)) + 98} ::= \frac{1 \times ((5 \times 6) + (7 \times 2))}{(4 \times 30) + (9 - 8)} \\ &::= \frac{1 \times (5 - (6 - (7^2)))}{4 + (30 + 98)} ::= \frac{1 - (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 2)))}{4 - (3 \times (0 - (9 \times 8)))} ::= \frac{(1 + ((5 + 6) \times 7)) \times 2}{430 - (9 - 8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{16485}{23079} &::= \frac{1 \times (6 - (4 - (8 - 5)))}{2 + (3 + (0 - (7 - 9)))} ::= \frac{1 \times (6 - (4 - (8 + 5)))}{2 + (3 - (0 - (7 + 9)))} ::= \frac{1 + (64 - (8 \times 5))}{2 - (30 - (7 \times 9))} ::= \frac{(1^{64}) \times (8 \times 5)}{2 \times (30 + (7 - 9))} \\ &::= \frac{((1^{64}) + 8) \times 5}{(2 - 3) \times (0 - (7 \times 9))} ::= \frac{1 \times ((6 + (4 - 8)) \times 5)}{2 - ((3 \times (0 - 7)) + 9)} ::= \frac{1 - ((6 \times (4 - 8)) + 5)}{2 \times (30 - (7 + 9))} ::= \frac{1 \times ((6 + 48) \times 5)}{2 \times (3 \times ((07 \times 9)))} \\ &::= \frac{1 \times (6 \times ((4 + 8) \times 5))}{(2^3 + 0) \times (7 \times 9)} ::= \frac{1 + (6 + (48 + 5))}{2 + (3 - (0 - 79))} ::= \frac{1 \times (6 \times (48 \times 5))}{(2 + 30) \times (7 \times 9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{17460}{82935} &::= \frac{1 - (7 - (4 + (6 - 0)))}{((8 - 2) \times 9) - 35} ::= \frac{(1 - 7) \times (4 - (6 - 0))}{8 + ((2 \times (9 \times 3)) - 5)} ::= \frac{(1 + (7 - 4)) \times (6 - 0)}{82 + ((9 \times 3) + 5)} ::= \frac{1 + (7 + (4 \times (6 - 0)))}{8 \times (2 + (9 + (3 + 5)))} \\ &::= \frac{(17 \times 4) - 60}{8 - (2 - ((9 \times 3) + 5))} ::= \frac{1 + (7 - (4 - 60))}{8 \times (((2 + 9) \times 3) + 5)} ::= \frac{1 \times (74 + (6 - 0))}{(82 - (9 - 3)) \times 5} ::= \frac{((1 + 7) \times 4) + 60}{(8 \times (2 \times (9 \times 3))) + 5} \\ &::= \frac{1 \times (7 \times (4 \times (6 - 0)))}{(8^2) + ((9^3) + 5)} ::= \frac{(17 - 4) \times 60}{((82 \times 9) + 3) \times 5} ::= \frac{(1^74) \times 60}{(8 + (2 + 9)) \times (3 \times 5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{19350}{27864} &:= \frac{1 + (9 + (3 \times (5 - 0)))}{2^{7-8+6} + 4} := \frac{((1+9)^3) + 50}{27 \times ((8+6) \times 4)} := \frac{(1^{93}) \times 50}{2 + (7 \times (8 + (6 - 4)))} := \frac{1 \times ((9+3) \times 50)}{27 \times (8 + (6 \times 4))} \\ &:= \frac{(1^9) \times (3 \times 50)}{27 \times ((8-6) \times 4)} := \frac{((1^9) + 3) \times 50}{278 + (6 + 4)} := \frac{1 \times ((9-3) \times 50)}{27 \times (8 \times (6-4))} := \frac{1 \times (9 \times (3 \times 50))}{27 \times (8 + 64)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (9 - 3)) \times 50}{((2^7) - (8 - 6)) \times 4} := \frac{((1+9)^3) - 50}{((2+7) \times 8) + (6^4)} := \frac{(1+9) \times (3 \times 50)}{27 \times (8 \times (6+4))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{19584}{36720} &:= \frac{1 \times ((9 + (5 - 8)) \times 4)}{3 \times (6 + (7 + (2 - 0)))} := \frac{1 - ((9 \times (5 - 8)) - 4)}{3 \times (6 + (7 \times (2 - 0)))} := \frac{1 \times ((9 - (5 - 8)) \times 4)}{3 \times (6 \times (7 - (2 - 0)))} := \frac{1 - (9 \times (5 - (8 + 4)))}{3 \times ((6 \times 7) - (2 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (9 - (5 - 84))}{3 + (6 \times (7 + 20))} := \frac{(1^9) \times (58 \times 4)}{3 + (6 \times (72 - 0))} := \frac{(1+9) \times ((5 \times 8) - 4)}{3 + (672 - 0)} := \frac{(1+95) \times (8 - 4)}{(3^6) - (7 + (2 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (95 + 8)) \times 4}{3 \times ((6+7) \times 20)} := \frac{(1 + (9 + 5)) \times (8 \times 4)}{(3 + (6 \times 7)) \times 20} := \frac{(19 + 5) \times (8 - 4)}{36 \times (7 - (2 - 0))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{19764}{23058} &:= \frac{1 \times (9 - (7 - (6 + 4)))}{2 \times ((3 \times (05)) - 8)} := \frac{1 \times (9 + (7 + (6 - 4)))}{(2^3 + 0) + (5 + 8)} := \frac{1 - (9 - ((7 \times 6) - 4))}{2 + (30 - (5 - 8))} := \frac{1 \times (9 \times ((7 - 6) \times 4))}{(2 \times (30 - 5)) - 8} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (9 - (7 \times (6 - 4)))}{2 - (3 + ((0 \times 5) - 8))} := \frac{1 + ((9 \times 7) - (6 + 4))}{2 + (3 - (0 - 58))} := \frac{1 - (9 - (76 + 4))}{(2 - 30) \times (5 - 8)} := \frac{(19 - 7) \times (6 + 4)}{2 \times (30 + (5 \times 8))} \\ &:= \frac{(19 - 7)^{6-4}}{((2+30) \times 5) + 8} := \frac{(1 + (9 - 7)) \times 64}{(23 - (0 - 5)) \times 8} := \frac{(1+9) \times (7 \times (6 \times 4))}{(2 + (3^{05})) \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{21468}{59037} &:= \frac{2 \times (1 \times (4 - (6 - 8)))}{5 - (9 + (0 - 37))} := \frac{2 + (1 \times (4 + (6 + 8)))}{(5 \times (9 - 0)) + (3 + 7)} := \frac{(2 \times (1 \times (4 + 6))) + 8}{(5 + (9 + (0 - 3))) \times 7} := \frac{2 \times (1 \times (4 + (6 + 8)))}{5 + (90 - (3 - 7))} \\ &:= \frac{2 \times ((1 - (4 - 6)) \times 8)}{2 \times ((1 - (4 - 6)) \times 8)} := \frac{2 \times (1 \times ((4 + 6) \times 8))}{(2 + (1 + (4 \times 6))) \times 8} := \frac{(2 + (1 + (4 \times 6))) \times 8}{214 + (6 + 8)} \\ &:= \frac{5 + (90 + 37)}{(5 \times 90) - (3 + 7)} := \frac{590 - (3 - 7)}{590 + 37} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (1 \times (4 - (6 - 8)))}{59 + (0 - 37)} := \frac{(2 - (1 + (4 - 6))) \times 8}{(5 \times (9 - 0)) + (3 \times 7)} := \frac{2 + (146 + 8)}{(5 \times 90) - (3 \times 7)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{24651}{90387} &:= \frac{2 \times (4 + (6 - (5 - 1)))}{9 + (0 - ((3 - 8) \times 7))} := \frac{2^{4 \times (6-5)} - 1}{((9 + (0 - 3)) \times 8) + 7} := \frac{(2 - (4 - 6)) \times (5 + 1)}{90 - (3 - (8 - 7))} := \frac{2 - (4 - ((6 \times 5) - 1))}{9 - (0 - (3 + 87))} \\ &:= \frac{(2^{4+6-5}) + 1}{90 + (38 - 7)} := \frac{(2 \times ((4 \times 6) - 5)) + 1}{90 - (3 - (8 \times 7))} := \frac{(2 \times ((4 \times 6) + 5)) - 1}{(9 \times ((03 \times 8))) - 7} \\ &:= \frac{(24 - 6) \times (5 + 1)}{9 - (0 - 387)} := \frac{2 + ((46 \times 5) - 1)}{903 - (8 \times 7)} := \frac{2 + (4 \times ((6 \times 5) + 1))}{(90 - (3 \times 8)) \times 7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{24857}{39061} &:= \frac{2 - (4 + (8 \times (5 - 7)))}{(3 \times (9 - 0)) - (6 - 1)} := \frac{(2 + (4 - (8 - 5))) \times 7}{(3 \times (9 - 0)) + (6 \times 1)} := \frac{2 \times (4 + (8 - (5 - 7)))}{(3 \times (9 - (0 - 6))) - 1} := \frac{2 - (4 - (8 + 57))}{3 + (90 + (6 \times 1))} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (4 + (85 + 7))}{3 + (90 + 61)} := \frac{((2 + 4) \times 8) + 57}{3 \times ((9 \times (06)) + 1)} := \frac{(2 + (4 + (8 + 5))) \times 7}{(3 \times 90) - 61} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times 4) - (8 - (5 \times 7))}{3 - (9 + (0 - 61))} := \frac{(2 - (4 - (8 - 5))) \times 7}{3 + (9 + ((0 \times 6) - 1))} := \frac{2 + (4 \times (8 - (5 - 7)))}{3 - (9 \times (0 - (6 + 1)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{27054}{93186} &:= \frac{2 + (7 - (0 \times 54))}{9 + (((3 - 1) \times 8) + 6)} := \frac{2 + (7 - (0 - (5 + 4)))}{((9 - (3 - 1)) \times 8) + 6} := \frac{27 - (0 \times 54)}{9 - (3 - (1 + 86))} := \frac{2 \times (7 - (0 - (5 \times 4)))}{93 \times (1 \times (8 - 6))} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (70 + (5 + 4))}{93 \times (1 + (8 - 6))} := \frac{(2 + 70) \times (5 + 4)}{93 \times (18 + 6)} := \frac{270 - 54}{(9^3) + (1 + (8 + 6))} := \frac{27 \times ((05 + 4))}{(9^3) + (18 \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + 70) \times 54}{9 \times (31 \times (8 \times 6))} := \frac{270 + 54}{93 \times (18 - 6)} := \frac{27 \times (054)}{9 \times (3 \times 186)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{27486}{50391} & := \frac{(2 \times (7 + (4 - 8))) + 6}{50 - ((3 \times 9) + 1)} := \frac{2 - ((7 \times (4 - 8)) + 6)}{5 - (0 - (39 \times 1))} := \frac{2 \times (7 + (4 \times (8 - 6)))}{5 \times ((03 + (9 - 1)))} := \frac{(2 - (7 - (4 + 8))) \times 6}{50 + (3 \times (9 \times 1))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times ((7 - 4) \times 8)) + 6}{5 - (0 - (3 + 91))} := \frac{2 \times (7 + (4 - (8 - 6)))}{5 - (0 - ((3 \times 9) + 1))} := \frac{(2^{7-4}) - (8 - 6)}{5 + (0 - (3 - (9 \times 1)))} := \frac{27 \times (4 \times (8 - 6))}{5 - (0 - 391)} \\
 & := \frac{(2 + (7 - 4)) \times (8 \times 6)}{5 \times (0 - (3 - 91))} := \frac{((2 \times 7) + 4)^{8-6}}{503 + 91} := \frac{2^{7+4-8} \times 6}{50 + (39 - 1)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29071}{45683} & := \frac{2 + (90 - 71)}{(4 + (5 - (6 - 8))) \times 3} := \frac{29 + ((0 \times 7) - 1)}{4 \times (5 - ((6 - 8) \times 3))} := \frac{29 - (0 - (7 - 1))}{4 + (56 - (8 - 3))} := \frac{(2 - 9) \times (0 - (7 - 1))}{((4 \times 5) - (6 - 8)) \times 3} \\
 & := \frac{(2 - 9) \times ((0 \times 7) - 1)}{4 - ((5 \times (6 - 8)) + 3)} := \frac{(2 - 9) \times (0 - (7 \times 1))}{4 + ((5 \times (6 + 8)) + 3)} := \frac{2 - (9 \times (0 - (7 - 1)))}{4 - (5 - (6 + 83))} := \frac{2 + (90 + (7 - 1))}{4 + (5 \times (6 \times (8 - 3)))} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times (90 - (7 - 1))}{4 \times (((5 \times 6) - 8) \times 3)} := \frac{2 \times (90 + 71)}{(4^5) - (6 + (8^3))} := \frac{(2^9 + 0) \times (7 \times 1)}{((4^5) \times 6) - (8^3)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29358}{67104} & := \frac{(2 \times (9 - (3 - 5))) - 8}{(6 \times (7 - (1 - 0))) - 4} := \frac{2 + (9 - (3 - (5 + 8)))}{6 \times (7 + (1^{04}))} := \frac{2 - ((9 \times (3 - 5)) - 8)}{67 + (1 + (0 - 4))} := \frac{29 + (3 - (5 - 8))}{6 + ((7 \times 10) + 4)} \\
 & := \frac{2 + (9 \times (3 - (5 - 8)))}{((6 \times 7) - 10) \times 4} := \frac{(2 - 9) \times (3 \times (5 - 8))}{6 \times ((7 - (1 - 0)) \times 4)} := \frac{29 - (3 - 58)}{6 \times ((7 + (1 - 0)) \times 4)} := \frac{((2 + 9) \times 3) + 58}{((6 \times 7) + 10) \times 4} \\
 & := \frac{(2 + (9 + 3)) \times (5 + 8)}{(6 \times (7 \times 10)) - 4} := \frac{(2^9) - (3 - 58)}{6^{7+1-04}} := \frac{(2 \times 935) - 8}{(6 \times 710) - 4}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29403}{81675} & := \frac{2 \times (9 \times (40^3))}{(8 - (1 - (6 + 7)))^5} := \frac{(2 - (9 - 4)) \times (0 - 3)}{8 - (1 - (6 + (7 + 5)))} := \frac{2 + (9 + (4 - (0 - 3)))}{8 + (1 + (6 + (7 \times 5)))} := \frac{2 - (9 - (40 + 3))}{(8 - (1 - (6 + 7))) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{(2 + (9 + (4 - 0))) \times 3}{8 + ((16 \times 7) + 5)} := \frac{2 + (9 + (40 + 3))}{(8 - (1 \times 6)) \times 75} := \frac{2 \times (9 \times (4 - (0 \times 3)))}{8 + (16 \times (7 + 5))} := \frac{(2 - (9 - 40)) \times 3}{((8 \times (1 \times 6)) + 7) \times 5} \\
 & := \frac{2 \times (9 \times (4 \times (03)))}{(8 + (16 \times 7)) \times 5} := \frac{2 \times (9^{4+0 \times 3})}{81 \times (6 \times 75)} := \frac{2 + (940 + 3)}{(81 - 6) \times (7 \times 5)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{39520}{67184} & := \frac{(3 \times (9 - 5)) - (2 - 0)}{6 + (7 + (1 \times (8 - 4)))} := \frac{(3 \times 9) - (5 + (2 - 0))}{6 + (7 \times (1 \times (8 - 4)))} := \frac{3 + (9 \times (5 - (2 - 0)))}{6 - ((7 \times (1 - 8)) + 4)} := \frac{(3 \times (9 + 5)) - (2 - 0)}{(6 - (7 - 18)) \times 4} \\
 & := \frac{3 + ((9 \times 5) + (2 - 0))}{6 + (7 + (18 \times 4))} := \frac{((3 + 9) \times 5) + 20}{6 + ((7 \times 18) + 4)} := \frac{(3 + 9) \times (5 \times (2 - 0))}{((6 \times 7) + (1 + 8)) \times 4} := \frac{3 \times ((9 - 5) \times 20)}{6 \times (((7 + 1) \times 8) + 4)} \\
 & := \frac{(3 + 9) \times (5 + 20)}{6 + (7 \times (18 \times 4))} := \frac{(3 + (9 - 5)) \times 20}{((6 + 7) \times 18) + 4} := \frac{(3 + (9 + 5)) \times 20}{6 + ((71 \times 8) + 4)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{41832}{59760} & := \frac{4 + (1 + (8 + (3 - 2)))}{(5 \times (9 + 7)) - 60} := \frac{4 - (1 \times (8 - 32))}{5 \times (9 - (7 - (6 - 0)))} := \frac{4 - ((1^8) - 32)}{5 \times (9 + (7 - (6 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times (1 \times (8 + 3))) - 2}{5 \times ((9 - 7) \times (6 - 0))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times 18) - (3^2)}{5 + (9 + (76 - 0))} := \frac{4 + (1 + (8 \times (3^2)))}{5 \times (9 + (7 + (6 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times (1 + (8 \times 3))) - 2}{(5 \times (9 + 7)) + 60} := \frac{4 \times ((18 \times 3) + 2)}{5 \times ((9 - 7)^6 + 0)} \\
 & := \frac{(41 + 8) \times (3 \times 2)}{(5 + (9 - 7)) \times 60} := \frac{(4 + ((1^8) \times 3))^2}{(5 \times (9 - 7)) + 60} := \frac{4 + (1 + ((8 + 3)^2))}{(5 - (9 - 7)) \times 60}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{45136}{70928} & := \frac{4 - (5 \times (1 + (3 - 6)))}{7 - (0 - (9 - (2 - 8)))} := \frac{4 + (5 - ((1 - 3) \times 6))}{7 - (0 - ((9 \times 2) + 8))} := \frac{4 \times (5 - (1 + (3 - 6)))}{7 - (0 - (9 + 28))} := \frac{4 - (5 - (1 \times 36))}{70 - (9 - (2 - 8))} \\
 & := \frac{4 + (5 \times (1 \times (3 + 6)))}{70 - (9 - (2 \times 8))} := \frac{4 + (51 + 36)}{70 + ((9^2) - 8)} := \frac{(4 \times 5) + (13 \times 6)}{70 + (92 - 8)} := \frac{4 \times (5 + (1 + 36))}{((7 - (0 - 9))^2) + 8} \\
 & := \frac{(4^{5-1}) - (3 \times 6)}{(70 \times 9) - (2^8)} := \frac{451 + (3 - 6)}{(7 - (0 - (9^2))) \times 8} := \frac{451 + (3 \times 6)}{709 + 28}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{49320}{67815} &:= \frac{4 + (9 - (3 + (2 - 0)))}{6 - (7 - (8 - (1 - 5)))} := \frac{4 \times (9 - (3 - (2 - 0)))}{6 - (7 - ((8 + 1) \times 5))} := \frac{4 \times (9 + (3 - (2 - 0)))}{6 - (7 \times (8 - 15))} := \frac{4 \times ((9 - 3) \times (2 - 0))}{6 \times (7 + (8 + (1 - 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (9 + (3 + (2 - 0)))}{6 + ((7 \times 8) + 15)} := \frac{4 \times (9 + (3^2 + 0))}{6 + (7 + (81 + 5))} := \frac{4 \times (9 - (3 + (2 - 0)))}{6 - (7 - (8 + 15))} := \frac{4 \times (9 - (3 - 20))}{67 + (81 - 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (9 - 3)) \times 20}{(6 + (7 \times (8 - 1))) \times 5} := \frac{4^{9-3 \times (2+0)}}{6 + (78 - (1 - 5))} := \frac{(4 \times (9 - 3))^2 + 0}{6 + (781 + 5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{52610}{89437} &:= \frac{5 - (2 - (6 + (1 - 0)))}{8 + (9 - (4 + (3 - 7)))} := \frac{(5^2) - (6 - (1 - 0))}{8 + (9 - (4 - (3 \times 7)))} := \frac{5 \times (2 \times (6 - (1 - 0)))}{(8 + 9) \times ((4 \times 3) - 7)} := \frac{5 \times (2 \times (6 + (1 - 0)))}{(8 + (9 \times (4 - 3))) \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times (2 \times (6 \times 10))}{(8 + 94) \times (3 + 7)} := \frac{5 \times (26 \times (1 - 0))}{(((8 \times 9) + 4) \times 3) - 7} := \frac{(5 \times 26) + 10}{(8 + 9) \times (4 + (3 + 7))} := \frac{5 \times (2 \times (6 + 10))}{8 \times (9 + (4 + (3 \times 7)))} \\ &:= \frac{(5^2) - 6 \times 10}{(8 + 9) \times ((4 \times 3) + 7)} := \frac{5 \times ((2 + 6) \times 10)}{(8 + 9) \times (4 \times (3 + 7))} := \frac{5 \times (26 - 10)}{8 \times (9 + (4 - (3 - 7)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{53298}{76140} &:= \frac{5 + (3 - (2 - (9 - 8)))}{7 + (6 + (1 - (4 - 0)))} := \frac{5 - (3 - ((2 \times 9) + 8))}{7 - (6 + (1 - 40))} := \frac{(5 \times 3) + (2 \times (9 + 8))}{7 \times (6 + (1 \times (4 - 0)))} := \frac{53 + (2 + (9 - 8))}{(7 - (6 - 1)) \times 40} \\ &:= \frac{53 + ((2 \times 9) - 8)}{76 + (14 - 0)} := \frac{5 - (3 + (2 - 98))}{7 \times (6 + (14 - 0))} := \frac{(5 - (3 - 2)) \times 98}{(7 + (6 + 1)) \times 40} := \frac{(5 + (3 + 2)) \times 98}{7 \times ((6 - 1) \times 40)} \\ &:= \frac{((5 \times 3) - 2) \times 98}{(7 + 6) \times 140} := \frac{(5 + (3^2)) \times 98}{7 \times ((6 + 1) \times 40)} := \frac{(53 - (2 + 9)) \times 8}{(7 + (6 - 1)) \times 40} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{53460}{81972} &:= \frac{534 + (6 - 0)}{819 + (7 + 2)} := \frac{5 \times ((3 \times 4) - (6 - 0))}{(8 - (1 - (9 + 7))) \times 2} := \frac{5 + (34 + (6 - 0))}{8 + (1 \times ((9 \times 7) - 2))} := \frac{5 \times ((3 \times 4) + (6 - 0))}{(8 \times (1 + (9 + 7))) + 2} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times ((3^4) - 60)}{(8 \times 19) + (7 + 2)} := \frac{(5 \times (3 \times 4)) + 60}{8 \times (1 \times (9 + (7 \times 2)))} := \frac{5 \times (3 + (4 \times (6 - 0)))}{8 + (197 + 2)} := \frac{5 \times (3 + (4 \times 60))}{81 \times (9 + (7 \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + (3 - 4)) \times 60}{8 \times (1 + (9 \times (7 - 2)))} := \frac{(5 \times (3^4)) - 60}{(8 - (1 - (9 + 7)))^2} := \frac{5 \times (3 \times (4 + 60))}{((81 \times 9) + 7) \times 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{58374}{60912} &:= \frac{(5 \times 8) - ((3 \times 7) - 4)}{6 - (0 - (9 \times (1 \times 2)))} := \frac{5 + (8 + (3 \times (7 + 4)))}{6 \times ((09 - (1^2)))} := \frac{(5 + (8 + (3 + 7))) \times 4}{6 \times (((09 - 1) \times 2))} := \frac{((5 + 8)^3) + (7 + 4)}{(6 \times ((09 - 1)))^2} \\ &:= \frac{5 + (8 + (37 \times 4))}{60 + (9 \times 12)} := \frac{((5 + (8 \times 3)) \times 7) + 4}{6^{-09+12}} := \frac{5 - (8 \times (3 - (7 + 4)))}{6 \times ((09 + (1 + 2)))} := \frac{5 + (8 \times (3 + 74))}{6 \times ((09 \times 12))} \\ &:= \frac{5 + ((8^3) - (7 + 4))}{(60 \times 9) - 12} := \frac{5 \times (8 + (3 \times (7 \times 4)))}{60 \times (9 - (1^2))} := \frac{5 \times (8 + (3 \times 74))}{60 \times ((9 + 1) \times 2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{79065}{81324} &:= \frac{7 \times ((9 \times (0 \times 6)) + 5)}{8 + (1 + (3 + 24))} := \frac{(7^{9-06}) \times 5}{((8 + 13)^2) \times 4} := \frac{7 \times (9 - (0 - (6 - 5)))}{8 \times (1 \times (3 + (2 + 4)))} := \frac{7 \times ((9 + (0 - 6)) \times 5)}{81 + (3 + 24)} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (90 \times (6 - 5))}{8 \times (((1^3) + 2)^4)} := \frac{7 \times (90 - (6 \times 5))}{(8 + 1) \times (3 \times (2^4))} := \frac{7 \times (9 - (0 - (6 + 5)))}{8 \times (1 \times (3 \times (2 + 4)))} := \frac{7 \times (90 - 65)}{(8 + 1) \times ((3 + 2) \times 4)} \\ &:= \frac{7 \times (9 \times ((0 \times 6) + 5))}{((8 + (1^3))^2) \times 4} := \frac{7 \times (9 \times ((06 \times 5)))}{81 \times (3 \times (2 \times 4))} := \frac{(7 + (90 - 6)) \times 5}{(81 - 3) \times (2 + 4)} \end{aligned}$$

• Four Digit's Numerator

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{3087}{129654} &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + 8)) - 7}{((12 + 9) \times ((6 \times 5) + 4))} := \frac{(3 - ((0 \times 8) - 7))}{(12 \times (9 + (6 + (5 \times 4))))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (8 + 7)))}{((1 - (2 - (9 + 6))) \times 54)} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (8 - 7)))}{((1 + (2 + (9 + (6 \times 5)))) \times 4)} \\ &:= \frac{(3 - (0 \times 87))}{(1 \times (2 \times (9 \times (6 + (5 - 4)))))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - 87))}{(1 + (29 + (6 \times (5^4))))} := \frac{(3 \times ((0 \times 8) + 7))}{(1 \times ((2 + 96) \times (5 + 4)))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (8 + 7)))}{(1 + ((29 \times 65) + 4))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (0 - (8 - 7)))}{((1 + (2 \times (9 + (6 - 5)))) \times 4)} := \frac{(30 - (8 + 7))}{(1 \times (2 + (9 - (6 - (5^4)))))} := \frac{(30 \times (8 - 7))}{(12 \times (96 + (5 + 4)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3654}{127890} := \frac{(3 - ((6 - 5)^4))}{((1^2) + (78 - (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 - (6 - (5 + 4)))}{(1 \times (2 \times (7 + (8 + 90))))} := \frac{(3 \times (6 \times (5 - 4)))}{((1 + ((2 \times 7) - 8)) \times 90)} := \frac{(3 \times (6 + (5 - 4)))}{(1 + ((2 \times 7) + (8 \times 90)))}$$

$$:= \frac{3^{(6-5)^4}}{((1^2) \times (7 + (8 + 90)))} := \frac{(3 + (6 \times (5 - 4)))}{(1 \times ((27 + 8) \times (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 + (6 + (5 \times 4)))}{(1 \times (((2^7) \times 8) - (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(36 - (5 + 4))}{((12 \times 78) + (9 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(36 - (5 - 4))}{(1 + (((2^7) + 8) \times (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(36 \times (5 - 4))}{((1 - (2 - (7 + 8))) \times 90)} := \frac{(36 + 54)}{(1 \times ((27 + 8) \times 90))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{3756}{108924} := \frac{(3 - 7) \times (5 - 6)}{(10 + (8 + (9 + 2))) \times 4} := \frac{(3 - (7 - 5)) \times 6}{1 \times (((089 \times 2) - 4))} := \frac{3 - (7 \times (5 - 6))}{10 + (((8 \times 9) - 2) \times 4)} := \frac{(3 \times (7 - 5)) + 6}{1 \times (((089 - 2) \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{3 \times (7 + (5 - 6))}{10 + 8^9 - 2 - 4} := \frac{(3^{7-5}) - 6}{1 \times ((089 + (2 - 4)))} := \frac{(3 \times 7) + (5 - 6)}{(1 - (0 - (8 \times (9 \times 2)))) \times 4} := \frac{(3 + (7 - 5)) \times 6}{10 \times (89 + (2 - 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (7 - 5))^6}{(1^{08}) + ((9 - 2) \times 4)} := \frac{3 + (7 + (5 \times 6))}{(1 - (0 - ((8 + 9)^2))) \times 4} := \frac{3 \times (7 - (5 - 6))}{(10 \times ((8 \times 9) - 2)) - 4}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{4021}{357869} := \frac{((4 \times (0 + 2)) + 1)}{(3 \times (((5 \times 7) + 8) \times 6) + 9))} := \frac{((4^{02}) - 1)}{(3 \times (5 \times ((7 \times (8 + 6)) - 9)))} := \frac{((40 \times 2) + 1)}{((3 + (57 \times (8 + 6))) \times 9)} := \frac{(4 - (0 - (2 \times 1)))}{(3 + ((57 + (8 - 6)) \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - (0 - (2 - 1)))}{(((3 + 5) \times (7 \times 8)) + (6 - 9))} := \frac{(4 - (0 \times 21))}{(((3^5) - (7 - (8 \times (6 + 9)))))} := \frac{(4 \times (0 + (2 \times 1)))}{((3 + 5) \times ((7 \times (8 + 6)) - 9))} := \frac{(4 + (0 - (2 \times 1)))}{(3 + (5 \times (7 \times (8 + (6 - 9)))))} \\ := \frac{(4 + (0 - (2 + 1)))}{(3 + (5 + ((7 + (8 - 6)) \times 9)))} := \frac{(4 + (0 - (2 - 1)))}{(3 \times (5 + (7 + (8 + 69))))} := \frac{(40 + (2 + 1))}{(((3^5) + (7 \times ((8 - 6)^9)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{5463}{180279} := \frac{(((5 \times 4) - 6) \times 3)}{((1 + ((80 \times 2) - 7)) \times 9)} := \frac{((5 - (4 - 6)) \times 3)}{((1 + (8 - (0 - 2))) \times (7 \times 9))} := \frac{((5 \times 4) - (6 \times 3))}{(1 \times ((8^{02}) - (7 - 9)))} := \frac{((5 + (4 - 6)) \times 3)}{(18 - (0 - 279))}$$

$$:= \frac{((5 - 4) \times (6 - 3))}{(1 + (80 + (2 + (7 + 9))))} := \frac{((5 - 4)^{6-3})}{(1 - (8 \times (0 - (2 - (7 - 9)))))} := \frac{5^{4-6+3}}{(1 - ((80 + 2) \times (7 - 9)))} := \frac{(5 + (4 - (6 - 3)))}{(1 \times ((8 - (0 - (2 \times 7))) \times 9))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (4^{6-3}))}{(((18^{02}) \times 7) + 9)} := \frac{(5 + (4 + (6 + 3)))}{(1 \times ((80 - (2 \times 7)) \times 9))} := \frac{(54 + (6 - 3))}{((1 + (80 + (2^7))) \times 9)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{5691}{438207} := \frac{((5 \times 6) - (9 - 1))}{((4 - (3 \times 82)) \times (0 - 7))} := \frac{((5 \times 6) + (9 + 1))}{(((438 + (2 - 0)) \times 7)} := \frac{((5 \times 6) + (9 - 1))}{(((438 - 20) \times 7)} := \frac{(5 - (6 - (9 \times 1)))}{((4 + (3 \times (8 + 20))) \times 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - (6 - (9 + 1)))}{(((43 - 8) \times 20) - 7)} := \frac{(5 - (6 - (9 - 1)))}{(((4^3) \times 8) + (20 + 7))} := \frac{(5 \times (6 + (9 + 1)))}{(4 \times ((3 + 8) \times (20 \times 7)))} := \frac{(5 + (6 - (9 \times 1)))}{(4 - (3 - ((8 \times 20) - 7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (6 - (9 + 1)))}{(4 + (3 + ((8 + (2 - 0)) \times 7)))} := \frac{(5 + (6 - (9 - 1)))}{(4 + (((3 + 8) \times 20) + 7))} := \frac{(569 \times 1)}{(43820 - 7)}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{6048}{175392} := \frac{((6 \times (0 \times 4)) + 8)}{(1 - (7 + (5 - (3 \times (9^2)))))} := \frac{((6 + (0 - 4)) \times 8)}{(1 + ((7 \times 53) + 92))} := \frac{(6 - ((0 \times 4) - 8))}{((1 + (7 + (5 \times 39))) \times 2)} := \frac{(6 - (0 - (4 + 8)))}{(1 + (7 + (((5 - 3)^9) + 2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 - (0 - (4 - 8)))}{(1 + (7 + (5 \times (3 + (9 - 2)))))} := \frac{(6 - (0 \times 48))}{(1 \times ((75 + (3 + 9)) \times 2))} := \frac{(6 \times ((0 \times 4) + 8))}{(17 + ((5^3) \times (9 + 2)))} := \frac{(6 + (0 - (4 - 8)))}{(1 \times ((7 \times 53) - (9^2)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(60 - (4 - 8))}{((1 + 7) \times (((5^3) - 9) \times 2))} := \frac{(60 + (4 - 8))}{(1 \times (7 \times (((5^3) - 9) \times 2)))} := \frac{(60 - 48)}{(1 \times ((7 + 5) \times ((3 \times 9) + 2)))}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{6174}{259308} := \frac{((6 \times (1 + 7)) + 4)}{(2 + 5) \times ((9 + 30) \times 8)} := \frac{((6 \times (1 + 7)) - 4)}{((2 - (5 - 9)) \times 308)} := \frac{(6 - ((1^7) + 4))}{(2 - (5 + (9 \times (3 + (0 - 8)))))} := \frac{(6 - (1 - (7 \times 4)))}{((2 + 5) \times (9 \times (30 - 8)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 - (1 - (7 + 4)))}{(2 \times ((5 + 9) \times (3 \times (0 + 8))))} := \frac{(6 - (1 - (7 - 4)))}{((2 \times (5 + 9)) + 308)} := \frac{(6 - (1 \times (7 - 4)))}{(25 + (93 - (0 - 8)))} := \frac{(6 - (1^7))}{(2 + ((5 - (9 - 30)) \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 - (1 + (7 - 4)))}{(2 \times ((5 + 9) \times (3 - (0 \times 8))))} := \frac{(6 + (1 \times (7 + 4)))}{(2 + ((59 + 30) \times 8))} := \frac{(6 + (1^7))}{((2^5) + ((9 \times 30) - 8))}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{6204}{193875} &:= \frac{((6 - (2 - 0)) \times 4)}{((1 + (9 + (3 + 87))) \times 5)} := \frac{(6 \times 20) + 4}{((1^9) \times 3875)} := \frac{((6^2 + 0) - 4)}{(1 + 9)^{3(8-7)^5}} := \frac{(6 - (2 + (0 - 4)))}{(1 \times (((9 \times 3) + 8) \times 7) + 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times (2 - (0 - 4)))}{((1 + (9 - (3 - 8))) \times 75)} := \frac{(6 \times (2 \times (0 + 4)))}{(1 \times ((9 + (3 + 8)) \times 75))} := \frac{(6 \times (2^{04}))}{((1 - 9) \times ((3 - 8) \times 75))} := \frac{(6 \times (20 + 4))}{((1 + 9) \times ((3 + 87) \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + (2 - (0 - 4)))}{((1 + (9 + (3 - 8))) \times 75)} := \frac{(6 + (2 + (0 - 4)))}{((((1^9) + 3) \times 8) - 7) \times 5} := \frac{(620 - 4)}{((19 + 3) \times 875)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{6915}{387240} &:= \frac{(((6 \times 9) + 1) \times 5)}{((387 - 2) \times 40)} := \frac{(6 - (9 - (1 + 5)))}{((3 - 87) \times (2 - (4 - 0)))} := \frac{(6 - (9 + (1 - 5)))}{(3 + (8 + (7 - (2 - 40))))} := \frac{(6 \times ((9 - 1) \times 5))}{(3 \times (8 \times (7 \times (2 \times 40))))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times (9 - (1 \times 5)))}{(3 \times (8 \times (7 \times (2 \times (4 - 0)))))} := \frac{(6 \times (9 - (1^5)))}{(3 \times (8 \times (7 \times (2^4 + 0))))} := \frac{(6 \times (9 - (1 + 5)))}{(3 \times (8 \times (7 \times (2 + (4 - 0)))))} := \frac{(6 \times (9 + (1 \times 5)))}{(3 \times (8 \times ((7^2) \times (4 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + ((9 - 1) \times 5))}{((3 \times 872) - 40)} := \frac{(6 + (9 + (1 + 5)))}{(3 \times (8 \times (7 + (2 + 40))))} := \frac{(6 + (9 + (1 - 5)))}{((3 + 8) \times (7 \times (2 \times (4 - 0))))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8046}{127395} &:= \frac{((8 - (0 - 4)) \times 6)}{(1 \times ((2 + (7 + 3)) \times 95))} := \frac{((8 + (0 - 4)) \times 6)}{(1 \times (((2^7) \times 3) - (9 - 5)))} := \frac{((80 + 4) \times 6)}{((1 + 27) \times (3 \times 95))} := \frac{((80 - 4) \times 6)}{((1 + (2 + 73)) \times 95)} \\ &:= \frac{(8 - (0 - (4 + 6)))}{(1 + (2 \times (7 + (3 \times (9 \times 5)))))} := \frac{(8 - (0 - (4 - 6)))}{(1 - (2 \times ((7 \times (3 - 9)) - 5)))} := \frac{(8 - (0 - 46))}{((1 + (2 \times (7 - 3))) \times 95)} := \frac{(8 \times ((0 \times 4) + 6))}{(1 \times (2 \times ((7 - 3) \times 95)))} \\ &:= \frac{(80 + (4 + 6))}{((12 + (7 \times 39)) \times 5)} := \frac{(80 + (4 - 6))}{((1 + (2 + (7 + 3))) \times 95)} := \frac{(80 + 46)}{((1 + (2 \times (7 + 3))) \times 95)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8257}{140369} &:= \frac{((8 - (2 + 5)) \times 7)}{(1 + ((4^{03}) + (6 \times 9)))} := \frac{((8 - (2 + 5))^7)}{(1 + (4 + (0 - (3 - (6 + 9)))))} := \frac{((8 \times 2) + (5 \times 7))}{(((140 + 3) \times 6) + 9)} := \frac{(8 - ((2 \times 5) - 7))}{(1 \times (4 - (0 - ((3 + 6) \times 9))))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 - (2 - (5 - 7)))}{(1 + ((4^{03}) - (6 - 9)))} := \frac{(8 - (2 + (5 - 7)))}{(1 - ((4 \times (0 - 36)) + 9))} := \frac{(8 - (2 - 57))}{(((1 + (4 - 0))^3 - 6) \times 9)} := \frac{(8 + (2 - (5 - 7)))}{(1 - (4 + (0 - (3 \times 69))))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 + (2 + (5 + 7)))}{(1 + (4 - (0 - 369)))} := \frac{(8 + (25 - 7))}{(1 + ((40 + (3 + 6)) \times 9))} := \frac{(82 + (5 \times 7))}{((1 - 40) \times (3 - (6 \times 9)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8345}{216970} &:= \frac{(((8 + 3) \times 4) + 5)}{(2 \times (1 + (6 + (9 \times 70))))} := \frac{((8 - (3 + 4))^5)}{(2 \times (1 + (6 \times (9 - (7 - 0)))))} := \frac{((8 \times (3 \times 4)) - 5)}{(2 \times (169 \times (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(8 - (3 - (4 \times 5)))}{(((2 + 1)^6) - (9 + 70))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 - (3 - (4 - 5)))}{(2 - (1 - (6 + (97 - 0))))} := \frac{(8 + ((3 - 4) \times 5))}{(2 + (1 \times (69 + (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(8 + (3 - (4 + 5)))}{(((2 + 1) \times (6 + 9)) + (7 - 0))} := \frac{(8 + (3 \times (4 - 5)))}{((2 \times (1 + 6)) + (9 - (7 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 + (3 + 45))}{((21 \times 69) + (7 - 0))} := \frac{(8 + (34 + 5))}{(((2 \times (1 + 6)) \times 9) + 70)} := \frac{(83 - 45)}{(2 + (16 + 970))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8659}{147203} &:= \frac{(((8 - 6) \times 5) - 9)}{1 + 4^{7-2-03}} := \frac{((8 \times 6) - (5 \times 9))}{(1 \times ((4 - (7 - 20)) \times 3))} := \frac{(8 - ((6 - 5)^9))}{(1 + (((4 + 7)^2 + 0) - 3))} := \frac{(8 - (6 - (5 \times 9)))}{(1 \times (47 \times (20 - 3)))} \\ &:= \frac{8^{(6-5)^9}}{(1 - ((4 - (7^2 + 0)) \times 3))} := \frac{(8 + ((6 \times 5) - 9))}{((1 + (4 \times 7)) \times (20 - 3))} := \frac{(8 + ((6 - 5) \times 9))}{(1 + (4 \times (72 - (0 \times 3))))} := \frac{(8 + ((6 - 5)^9))}{(147 - (2 \times (0 - 3)))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 + (6 + (5 + 9)))}{(1 \times (4 \times (7 \times (20 - 3))))} := \frac{(8 + (6 + (5 - 9)))}{(147 + (20 + 3))} := \frac{(86 - (5 \times 9))}{(((1 + 4) \times (7 \times 20)) - 3)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8749}{306215} &:= \frac{(((8 - 7)^4) \times 9)}{(3 \times ((0 \times 6) + (21 \times 5)))} := \frac{(((8 - 7)^4)^9)}{(3 - (0 - (6 + (21 + 5))))} := \frac{((8 \times (7 - 4)) - 9)}{(3 \times (0 + (((6^2) - 1) \times 5)))} := \frac{((8 \times 7) - 49)}{((30 \times (6 + (2 \times 1))) + 5)} \\ &:= \frac{((8 + 7) \times (4 \times 9))}{(30 \times (6 \times (21 \times 5)))} := \frac{((8 - 7) \times (4 \times 9))}{(30 \times (6 \times (2 + (1 \times 5))))} := \frac{((8 - 7) \times (4 + 9))}{((30 + (62 - 1)) \times 5)} := \frac{(8 - (7 - (4 \times 9)))}{(((30 + 6)^2) - (1^5))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 - (7 + (4 - 9)))}{(3 \times (0 + (6 + (2 \times (1 + 5)))))} := \frac{(8 + ((7 \times 4) - 9))}{(3 \times (0 + ((62 + 1) \times 5)))} := \frac{(8 + (7 - (4 + 9)))}{(3 - (0 - (62 + (1 \times 5))))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9078}{154326} &:= \frac{((9 + (0 - 7)) \times 8)}{((1 - (5 + (4^3))) \times (2 - 6))} := \frac{((9 + (0 - 7))^8)}{((1 + 543) \times (2 + 6))} := \frac{(9 - ((0 \times 7) - 8))}{(1 + ((54 - (3 \times 2)) \times 6))} := \frac{(9 - (0 - (7 + 8)))}{((1 + (5 + ((4^3) - 2))) \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(9 - (0 - (7 - 8)))}{(1 + (5 \times (4 - (3 - 26))))} := \frac{(9 - (0 \times 78))}{(1 + ((5 - 43) \times (2 - 6)))} := \frac{(9 - (0 - 78))}{(1543 - (2^6))} := \frac{(9 + ((0 \times 7) - 8))}{(1 + (5 + (4 + (3 - (2 - 6)))))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 + (0 - (7 - 8)))}{(1 \times (5 \times (4 + ((3 + 2) \times 6))))} := \frac{(90 - (7 - 8))}{(1543 - (2 - 6))} := \frac{(90 - 78)}{((1 + (5 - (4 - 32))) \times 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9153}{284760} &:= \frac{((9 + 15)^3)}{((2^8) \times (4 \times (7 \times 60)))} := \frac{((91 + 5)^3)}{(28 \times ((4^7) \times 60))} := \frac{(9 \times (1 \times (5 + 3)))}{(28 \times (4 + (76 - 0)))} := \frac{(9 \times (1 \times (5 - 3)))}{((2^8) + (4 \times (76 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 \times (1 + (5 - 3)))}{(((2 \times 8) + 4) \times (7 \times (6 - 0)))} := \frac{(9 \times (15 - 3))}{(2 \times ((8 - 4) \times (7 \times 60)))} := \frac{(9 \times (1 \times (5 - 3)))}{((2 + (8 - 4)) \times (7 \times 60))} := \frac{(9 \times (1 + (5 - 3)))}{((2 + (8 \times 47)) \times 60)} \\ &:= \frac{(9 + (15 \times 3))}{((2 + 8) \times (4 \times (7 \times (6 - 0))))} := \frac{(9 + 153)}{(((2 \times 8) - 4) \times (7 \times 60))} := \frac{(91 + (5^3))}{((2^{8-4}) \times (7 \times 60))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9167}{320845} &:= \frac{(((9 - 1) \times 6) + 7)}{((3 \times (20 \times (8 \times 4))) + 5)} := \frac{(9 - ((1^6) + 7))}{3 + 2^{0 \times 84 + 5}} := \frac{(9 - ((1^6) - 7))}{((3 \times (20 \times 8)) + 45)} := \frac{(9 - ((1 - 6) \times 7))}{((320 - (8 + 4)) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(9 - (1 - (6 + 7)))}{(3 \times ((20 \times (8 + 4)) + 5))} := \frac{(9 - (1 - (6 - 7)))}{(((3 \times (20 \times (8 - 4))) + 5)} := \frac{(9 \times ((1^6) + 7))}{(3 \times (2 \times (0 + (84 \times 5))))} := \frac{(9 \times (1 - (6 - 7)))}{(((3 + (2 - (0 \times 8)))^4) + 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(9 + ((1^6) - 7))}{(3 \times (((2 - (0 - 8)) \times 4) - 5))} := \frac{(9 + (1 \times (6 - 7)))}{(((3 \times 20) - (8 - 4)) \times 5)} := \frac{(91 - 67)}{(3 + ((208 \times 4) + 5))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9342}{105876} &:= \frac{((9 + 3) \times (4 - 2))}{((1 + (0 - 5)) \times (8 - 76))} := \frac{((9 - 3) \times 42)}{((10 + 58) \times (7 \times 6))} := \frac{(9 - (3 - (4 + 2)))}{((1 + (0 - 5)) \times (8 - (7 \times 6)))} := \frac{(9 - (3 \times (4 - 2)))}{(((1 + (0 - (5 - 8))) \times 7) + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(9 \times ((3 + 4)^2))}{(((105 \times 8) - 7) \times 6)} := \frac{(9 \times (3 + (4 - 2)))}{((10 + (5 \times (8 + 7))) \times 6)} := \frac{(9 + (3 - (4 + 2)))}{(1 - (0 - (5 + ((8 \times 7) + 6))))} := \frac{(9 + (3 \times (4 + 2)))}{(1 \times (0 - ((5 - (8 \times 7)) \times 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 + (3 \times (4 - 2)))}{(1 \times (0 - (5 \times (8 - (7 \times 6)))))} := \frac{(9 + (3^{4-2}))}{((1 - (0 - ((5 \times 8) - 7))) \times 6)} := \frac{(9 + (3 + 42))}{((10 + (5 + 87)) \times 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9786}{342510} &:= \frac{(((9 - 7) \times 8) - 6)}{((3 + ((4 - 2)^5)) \times 10)} := \frac{(9 - (7 - (8 \times 6)))}{((3 + 4) \times (25 \times 10))} := \frac{(9 - (7 - (8 + 6)))}{(((3^4) - 25) \times 10)} := \frac{(9 - (7 - (8 - 6)))}{((3 + (4 + (2 + 5))) \times 10)} \\ &:= \frac{(9 \times (7 + (8 - 6)))}{((3^4) \times (25 + 10))} := \frac{(9 + ((7 - 8) \times 6))}{(3 \times (4 + ((2^5) - (1 - 0))))} := \frac{(9 + (7 - (8 + 6)))}{(3 + ((4^2) + (51 - 0)))} := \frac{(9 + (7 - (8 - 6)))}{(((3^4) - (2^5)) \times 10)} \\ &:= \frac{(9 + (7 + (8 \times 6)))}{((3 + 4) \times ((2^5) \times 10))} := \frac{(9 + (7 + (8 - 6)))}{(3 \times (42 \times (5 \times (1 - 0))))} := \frac{(97 - 86)}{((3 \times (4 \times (2^5))) + (1 - 0))} \end{aligned}$$

3.11 12 Equivalent Blocks

• Five Digit's Representations

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10857}{49632} &:= \frac{(1 + (0 - 8)) \times (5 - 7)}{4^{9-6 \times (3-2)}} := \frac{1 - (0 - (8 + (5 + 7)))}{4 \times (9 + (6 + (3^2)))} := \frac{1 + (0 - (8 - (5 \times 7)))}{(((4 \times 9) + 6) \times 3) + 2} := \frac{((1^{08}) + 5) \times 7}{4 \times ((9 \times 6) - (3 \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{(10 - 8) \times (5 \times 7)}{(4^{9-6}) \times (3 + 2)} := \frac{(108^5) \times 7}{(4 \times (9 \times 6))^{3+2}} := \frac{1 \times (((08 + 5) \times 7))}{(4 \times 96) + 32} := \frac{10 \times ((8 - 5) \times 7)}{((4 \times 9) - 6) \times 32} \\ &:= \frac{1 - (0 - (8 + (5 - 7)))}{4 \times (9 - (6 - (3 + 2)))} := \frac{(10 + (8 \times 5)) \times 7}{(49 - (6 + 3))^2} := \frac{1 \times (0 - (8 - 57))}{(4 + (9 - 6)) \times 32} := \frac{((10 + 8)^5) \times 7}{(4 \times (9 \times (6^3)))^2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10962}{37584} &:= \frac{1 - (0 - ((9 - 6) \times 2))}{3 \times (7 + (5 - (8 - 4)))} := \frac{1 - (0 - (9 + (6 - 2)))}{3 \times (7 + (5 + (8 - 4)))} := \frac{1 \times ((09 + (6 \times 2)))}{3 \times (7 + (5 + (8 + 4)))} := \frac{1 + (0 - (9 - (6^2)))}{(3 - (7 \times (5 - 8))) \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{((1^{09}) + 6)^2}{(37 + 5) \times (8 - 4)} := \frac{1 \times (((09 \times 6) + 2))}{3 - (7 \times (5 - (8 \times 4)))} := \frac{(1^{09}) + 62}{(3 - (7 - 58)) \times 4} := \frac{((10 + 9) \times 6) - 2}{(37 - 5) \times (8 + 4)} \\ &:= \frac{109 - (6 - 2)}{(3 + 7) \times ((5 \times 8) - 4)} := \frac{(10 \times 9) + (6^2)}{3 \times ((7 + 5) \times (8 + 4))} := \frac{((10 \times 9) - 6) \times 2}{((3 + 7) \times 58) - 4} := \frac{10 \times (96 + 2)}{3 \times (7 \times (5 \times (8 \times 4)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13257}{48609} & := \frac{1 \times (3 - (2 + (5 - 7)))}{4 - (8 - (6 - (0 - 9)))} := \frac{1 \times (3 + ((2 \times 5) - 7))}{4 + ((8 - (6 - 0)) \times 9)} := \frac{1 \times (3 \times ((2 \times 5) - 7))}{48 - (6 - (0 - 9))} := \frac{1 \times (3 \times (2 - (5 - 7)))}{4 \times (8 - (6 + (0 - 9)))} \\
 & := \frac{1 + (3 + (2 + (5 + 7)))}{4 + (8 - (6 \times (0 - 9)))} := \frac{1 \times (3 + (2 \times (5 + 7)))}{4 + (86 - (0 - 9))} := \frac{1 \times (3^{2-5+7})}{(48 \times (6 - 0)) + 9} := \frac{(1 + ((3 \times 2) + 5)) \times 7}{4 \times (8 + (60 + 9))} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times ((3^2) \times (5 + 7))}{(4 - (8 \times 6)) \times (0 - 9)} := \frac{((1 + 3) \times (2^5)) + 7}{486 - (0 - 9)} := \frac{(1 + 3) \times ((2^5) + 7)}{(4 \times 8) + (60 \times 9)} := \frac{1 + ((32 \times 5) + 7)}{4 + ((8 + 60) \times 9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13290}{58476} & := \frac{1 - (3 + (2 - (9 - 0)))}{5 + (8 - (4 - (7 + 6)))} := \frac{1 \times (3 - (2 - (9 - 0)))}{(5 \times 8) + (4 \times (7 - 6))} := \frac{13 + (2^9 + 0)}{5 \times ((84 - 7) \times 6)} := \frac{1 + (3 + (2 + (9 - 0)))}{5 + (8 + (47 + 6))} \\
 & := \frac{13 - (2 - (9 - 0))}{5 + (84 - (7 - 6))} := \frac{((1 + 3)^2) + (9 - 0)}{5 \times (((8 - 4) \times 7) - 6)} := \frac{1 \times ((3 + 2) \times (9 - 0))}{(5 + ((8 - 4) \times 7)) \times 6} := \frac{1 + ((3^2) + 90)}{5 \times (8 + (4 + 76))} \\
 & := \frac{13 + (2 + 90)}{(5 \times 84) + (7 \times 6)} := \frac{(1^3) \times 290}{58 \times ((4 \times 7) - 6)} := \frac{1 \times ((3 + 2)^9 + 0)}{(5^8) \times ((4 \times 7) - 6)} := \frac{1 \times (3 \times 290)}{58 \times ((4 + 7) \times 6)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13820}{79465} & := \frac{1 - (3 - (8 - (2 - 0)))}{7 + (9 - (4 - (6 + 5)))} := \frac{1 - (3 - (8 + (2 - 0)))}{(7 \times (9 - 4)) + (6 + 5)} := \frac{(1 - (3 - 8)) \times (2 - 0)}{((7 - (9 - 4))^6) + 5} := \frac{1 + (3 - (8 - 20))}{7 + ((9 \times (4 + 6)) - 5)} \\
 & := \frac{1 + (3 + (8 \times (2 - 0)))}{((7 + (9 + 4)) \times 6) - 5} := \frac{(1 + (3 + 8)) \times (2 - 0)}{(7 \times (9 + (4 + 6))) + 5} := \frac{1 \times ((3 \times 8) + 20)}{((7 + (9 \times 4)) \times 6) - 5} := \frac{1 \times (3 \times (8 \times (2 - 0)))}{7 + (9 + (4 \times 65))} \\
 & := \frac{((1 + 3) \times 8) + 20}{(7 \times ((9 \times 4) + 6)) + 5} := \frac{(1 + 3) \times (8 \times 20)}{(7 + 9) \times (46 \times 5)} := \frac{138 + (2 - 0)}{794 + (6 + 5)} := \frac{1 \times (3 \times (8^2 + 0))}{(7 + 9) \times (4 + 65)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14695}{38207} & := \frac{1 - (4 + (6 - (9 + 5)))}{3 + (8 + (2 - (0 \times 7)))} := \frac{(1 + (4 + (6 - 9))) \times 5}{3 + ((8 \times (2 - 0)) + 7)} := \frac{1 + (4 + (6 + (9 - 5)))}{3 \times (8 - (2 + (0 - 7)))} := \frac{1 + (4 - ((6 - 9) \times 5))}{38 - (2 \times (0 - 7))} \\
 & := \frac{1 + (4 + (6 + (9 + 5)))}{38 + (20 + 7)} := \frac{1 \times ((4 - (6 - 9)) \times 5)}{(3 \times (8 + 20)) + 7} := \frac{1 \times (4 + (6 + (9 \times 5)))}{(3 + 8) \times (20 - 7)} := \frac{(1 - (4 - (6 + 9))) \times 5}{3 + ((8 \times 20) - 7)} \\
 & := \frac{1 + ((4 \times 6) + (9 \times 5))}{((3 \times 8) + (2 - 0)) \times 7} := \frac{1 + ((4 \times 6) + 95)}{3 \times (8 \times (20 - 7))} := \frac{(1 + (46 - 9)) \times 5}{38 \times (20 - 7)} := \frac{(1 + (4 + (6 \times 9))) \times 5}{(38 \times 20) + 7}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15407}{63829} & := \frac{1 - (5 - (4 - (0 - 7)))}{6 - (3 - (8 + (2 \times 9)))} := \frac{(1 + (5 - (4 - 0))) \times 7}{6 - (3 - ((8^2) - 9))} := \frac{1 + (5 \times (4 - (0 \times 7)))}{6 + ((3 + (8 - 2)) \times 9)} := \frac{1 \times ((5 + (4 - 0)) \times 7)}{6 + ((3 \times 82) + 9)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (5 + (4 - 0))) \times 7}{((6 \times 3) - 8) \times 29} := \frac{(15 - (4 - 0)) \times 7}{(6 - (3 - 8)) \times 29} := \frac{(1 + (5 \times (4 - 0))) \times 7}{6 + ((3 + (8^2)) \times 9)} := \frac{154 - (0 - 7)}{638 + 29} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + 5) \times (4 \times (07))}{(6 - 3) \times (8 \times 29)} := \frac{1 \times (54 \times (07))}{6 + (3 \times (8 + (2^9)))} := \frac{1 \times ((5 + 40) \times 7)}{(63 + 82) \times 9} := \frac{(1 + (54 - 0)) \times 7}{(63 - 8) \times 29}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15930}{28674} & := \frac{(1 - (5 - 9)) \times (3 - 0)}{2 + (8 + (6 + (7 + 4)))} := \frac{1 \times (5 \times (9 - (3 - 0)))}{(2 \times 8) + ((6 \times 7) - 4)} := \frac{1 - (5 - (9 + 30))}{((2 + 8) \times 6) + (7 - 4)} := \frac{(1^5) + (9 + 30)}{2 \times ((8 - (6 - 7)) \times 4)} \\
 & := \frac{1 + (5 + (9 + 30))}{2 + (8 + (67 + 4))} := \frac{1 \times (5 \times (9 + (3 - 0)))}{2 \times (8 + ((6 \times 7) + 4))} := \frac{1 \times (5 \times (9^3 + 0))}{(2 + (8 + (6 - 7)))^4} := \frac{1 + (59 + 30)}{2 - (8 - (6 \times (7 \times 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{(15 \times 9) + 30}{286 + (7 + 4)} := \frac{(1 + 59) \times (3 - 0)}{(2 + (86 - 7)) \times 4} := \frac{(15 + 9) \times 30}{((2 - 8) \times (6 - 7))^4} := \frac{1 \times ((5 + 9) \times 30)}{((2^8) - 67) \times 4}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19764}{82350} & := \frac{1 \times (9 - (7 - (6 + 4)))}{8 - ((2^3) - 50)} := \frac{1 + (9 + (7 \times (6 - 4)))}{(8 - (2 \times 3)) \times 50} := \frac{1 \times (9 \times ((7 - 6) \times 4))}{(8 - (2 + 3)) \times 50} := \frac{1 - (9 - (7 \times (6 - 4)))}{8 + (2 + (3 \times (5 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{1 + (9 + ((7 \times 6) - 4))}{8 \times ((2 + 3) \times (5 - 0))} := \frac{1 + (97 + (6 + 4))}{(8 - (2 - 3)) \times 50} := \frac{(1^9) \times (7 \times (6 \times 4))}{(8 + (2 \times 3)) \times 50} := \frac{(1 + (9 - 7)) \times 64}{(8 + (2^3)) \times 50} \\
 & := \frac{1 \times (((9 \times 7) - 6) \times 4)}{((8 + 2)^3) - 50} := \frac{1 \times ((9 - 7) \times (6^4))}{((8 - 2)^3) \times 50} := \frac{(19 - 7) \times 64}{8 \times ((2^3) \times 50)} := \frac{1 - (97 - (6^4))}{((8 + 2)^3) \times (5 - 0)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25836}{71049} &:= \frac{(2^5) + (8-36)}{7 - (1 - (0 - (4-9)))} := \frac{2 - (5 - (8 - (3-6)))}{7 + (10 - (4-9))} := \frac{2 + (5 + (8 + (3-6)))}{7 - (10 - (4 \times 9))} := \frac{2^{5+8-3-6}}{7 + (1 - (0 - (4 \times 9)))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (5 + (8 + (3-6)))}{7 - (1 + (0 - 49))} := \frac{2 + (5 + (8 + (3+6)))}{7 + (10 + 49)} := \frac{(2 \times 5) + ((8 \times 3) - 6)}{((7+10) \times 4) + 9} := \frac{25 + (8 - (3-6))}{(7 - (1 \times (0-4))) \times 9} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (5 \times (8 + (3 \times 6)))}{710 - (4-9)} := \frac{258 + (3 \times 6)}{710 + 49} := \frac{(25 + (8+3)) \times 6}{((7 \times 10) - 4) \times 9} := \frac{2 \times ((5+8) \times (3 \times 6))}{((7 - (1-0))^4) - 9} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25963}{74180} &:= \frac{2 + (5 - (9 - (6+3)))}{7 + (4 + (1 + (8-0)))} := \frac{2 + ((5 \times (9-6)) - 3)}{7 + (41 - (8-0))} := \frac{2 \times (5 - (9 - (6 \times 3)))}{(7 + (4-1)) \times (8-0)} := \frac{2 + ((5 \times 9) + (6+3))}{(7 - (4+1)) \times 80} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times ((5+9) \times (6-3))}{(7 - (4 \times 1)) \times 80} := \frac{((2-5) \times 9) + (6^3)}{(7-4) \times 180} := \frac{2 \times (5 + ((9 \times 6) - 3))}{(7 - (4-1)) \times 80} := \frac{((25 \times 9) + 6) \times 3}{(7+4) \times 180} \\
 &:= \frac{2 + (5 \times (9 \times (6 \times 3)))}{(7^4) - (1+80)} := \frac{259 \times (6 \times 3)}{74 \times 180} := \frac{2 \times ((5+9) \times 63)}{7 \times (4 \times 180)} := \frac{((2 \times 59) - 6) \times 3}{(7 + (4+1)) \times 80} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29430}{76518} &:= \frac{2 - (9 - (4 \times (3-0)))}{7 - (6 - (5 - (1-8)))} := \frac{2 + (9 - (4 - (3-0)))}{7 + (6 - (5 - 18))} := \frac{2 \times (9 + (4 - (3-0)))}{(7+6) \times (5 - (1^8))} := \frac{(2 \times 9) + (4 + (3-0))}{7 + (65 + (1-8))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times ((9-4) \times (3-0))}{(7 \times (6 + (5-1))) + 8} := \frac{(2^{9-4}) + (3-0)}{7 - (6 - (5 \times 18))} := \frac{2 \times (9 - (4-30))}{(7+6) \times (5 + (1+8))} := \frac{2 + (9 + (4^3 + 0))}{(7 \times ((6 \times 5) - 1)) - 8} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (9-4)) \times 30}{7 \times (6 \times (5 + (1 \times 8)))} := \frac{2 \times ((9-4)^3 + 0)}{7 + (651 - 8)} := \frac{2 + (9 \times (4 + (3-0)))}{(7+6) \times (5 + (1 \times 8))} := \frac{(2 + (9+4)) \times 30}{(7+6) \times (5 \times 18)} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{34517}{98620} &:= \frac{3 - (4 - (5+17))}{(9 \times 8) - (6 \times (2-0))} := \frac{(3 - (4 - (5 \times 1))) \times 7}{(9 \times 8) + (6 + (2-0))} := \frac{3 + (4 + ((5-1) \times 7))}{((9+8) \times 6) - (2-0)} := \frac{3 + (4 + (5 \times (1 \times 7)))}{(9-8) \times (6 \times 20)} \\
 &:= \frac{3 + (4 + ((5+1) \times 7))}{(9 - (8-6)) \times 20} := \frac{3 + (45 + (1+7))}{98 + (62-0)} := \frac{3 \times ((4 \times 5) + (1^7))}{9 \times (8 + (6 \times (2-0)))} := \frac{(3 + (4 + (5-1))) \times 7}{(9 + (8-6)) \times 20} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times 4) + (5+1)) \times 7}{9 \times ((8-6) \times 20)} := \frac{(3 + (4 \times (5 \times 1))) \times 7}{(9 + (8+6)) \times 20} := \frac{3 - (4 \times (5 + (1-7)))}{(9 \times (8-6)) + (2-0)} := \frac{3 \times (((4 \times 5) - 1) \times 7)}{(9 + (8 \times 6)) \times 20} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{36708}{41952} &:= \frac{3 \times (6 - (7 + (0-8)))}{4 \times (1 \times (9 - (5-2)))} := \frac{36 + (7 + (0-8))}{4 \times ((1 + (9-5)) \times 2)} := \frac{3 \times (6 + (7 - (0-8)))}{((4 + (1+9)) \times 5) + 2} := \frac{3 + (67 - (0 \times 8))}{4 \times (1 + (9 + (5 \times 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{36 + (70-8)}{4 \times (1 + (9 \times (5-2)))} := \frac{(3-6) \times (7 \times (0-8))}{4 - ((1-95) \times 2)} := \frac{3 \times (6 \times (7 - (0 \times 8)))}{4 \times (((1^9) + 5)^2)} := \frac{(3^6) + (70-8)}{4 \times (1 + (9 \times (5^2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3^6) \times (7 \times (08))}{(4 \times (1 \times 9))^{5-2}} := \frac{3 + (670-8)}{4 \times (1 \times (95 \times 2))} := \frac{36 \times (7 \times (08))}{(4 - (1 - (9 \times 5)))^2} := \frac{(3+6) \times (7 \times (08))}{(4 \times ((1^9) + 5))^2} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{36712}{45890} &:= \frac{(3 - (6 - (7 \times 1))) \times 2}{4 + (5 - (8 - (9-0)))} := \frac{3 + (6 + (7+12))}{4 + ((5 \times 8) - (9-0))} := \frac{(36 - (7+1)) \times 2}{(4 \times (5 \times 8)) - 90} := \frac{3 \times (6 \times (7 - (1+2)))}{(4 + (5-8)) \times 90} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (67-1)) + 2}{(4 \times (5 \times 8)) + 90} := \frac{3 \times (6 \times ((7-1) \times 2))}{(45 \times 8) - 90} := \frac{(3+6) \times 712}{(4+5) \times 890} := \frac{36 \times (7 + (1+2))}{(45 \times 8) + 90} \\
 &:= \frac{36 \times (7 \times (1 \times 2))}{(4 - (5-8)) \times 90} := \frac{36 + 712}{45 + 890} := \frac{((3+6) \times (7+1))^2}{(4+5) \times (8 \times 90)} := \frac{3 \times (6 \times ((7+1)^2))}{4 \times (5 \times (8 \times (9-0)))} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{37085}{96421} &:= \frac{3 + (7 + ((0 \times 8) - 5))}{9 + (6 - (4 - (2 \times 1)))} := \frac{3 + (7 - ((0 \times 8) - 5))}{9 + (6 \times (4 + (2-1)))} := \frac{(3 - (7 + (0-8))) \times 5}{9 + (64 - 21)} := \frac{3 \times (7 - (0 - (8-5)))}{(9^{6-4}) - (2+1)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (7 - (0-8))) - 5}{9 + ((6 \times (4^2)) - 1)} := \frac{((3 + (7-0)) \times 8) - 5}{(9 \times (6 \times 4)) - 21} := \frac{(3 + (7 - (0-8))) \times 5}{9 \times ((6 \times 4) + (2 \times 1))} := \frac{(3 \times 70) - 85}{(9 \times (6^4-2)) + 1} \\
 &:= \frac{3 \times ((7 - (0-8)) \times 5)}{9 \times (64 + (2-1))} := \frac{(3 \times 70) + (8 \times 5)}{9 + (642 - 1)} := \frac{(3 - (7 \times (0-8))) \times 5}{(96 \times (4 \times 2)) - 1} := \frac{(3 + (7-0))^{8-5}}{9 + (((6^4) \times 2) - 1)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{45190}{76823} &:= \frac{4 + (5 + (1^9 + 0))}{7 - (6 - (8 + (2^3)))} := \frac{4 \times (5 \times (1^9 + 0))}{(7 \times 6) + (8 \times (2 - 3))} := \frac{(4 \times 5) + (1 + (9 - 0))}{(7 - (6 - (8 \times 2))) \times 3} := \frac{4 + ((5 - 1) \times (9 - 0))}{7 - (6 - ((8^2) + 3))} \\ &:= \frac{4 + (5 + (1 + 90))}{((7 \times 6) - 8) \times (2 + 3)} := \frac{(4 \times (5 \times 1)) + 90}{7 + (6 \times ((8 + 2) \times 3))} := \frac{4 - (5 - (1 + 90))}{((7 + 68) \times 2) + 3} := \frac{4 \times (5 \times (1 \times (9 - 0)))}{(((7 + 6) \times 8) - 2) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times (5 \times (1 + (9 - 0)))}{(76 - 8) \times (2 + 3)} := \frac{4 \times (5 \times 190)}{76 \times (82 + 3)} := \frac{4 \times (51 + (9 - 0))}{(76 - 8) \times (2 \times 3)} := \frac{451 + (9 - 0)}{((7 \times 6) - 8) \times 23} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{52730}{89641} &:= \frac{5 - ((2 - 7) \times (3 - 0))}{8 - (9 + (6 - 41))} := \frac{5 + (2 - (7 - 30))}{(8 + 9) \times (6 - (4 - 1))} := \frac{5 - (2 - (7 + 30))}{8 + ((9 + 6) \times (4 \times 1))} := \frac{527 + (3 - 0)}{896 + (4 + 1)} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times (2 + (7 + (3 - 0)))}{(8 \times 9) + (6 \times (4 + 1))} := \frac{(5 + 2) \times (7 + (3 - 0))}{89 + (6 \times (4 + 1))} := \frac{5 \times (2^{7-3+0})}{8 \times ((9 \times (6 - 4)) - 1)} := \frac{((5 \times 2) - 7) \times 30}{(8 \times (9 + (6 + 4))) + 1} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times (2 \times (7 + (3 - 0)))}{8 + (9 \times (6 \times (4 - 1)))} := \frac{(5 - 2) \times (7 \times 30)}{(8 + 9) \times (64 - 1)} := \frac{(5 - (2 - 7)) \times 30}{(8 + 9) \times (6 \times (4 + 1))} := \frac{(5^2) \times (7 + (3 - 0))}{(8 + 9) \times ((6 \times 4) + 1)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{54610}{92837} &:= \frac{(5 + 4) \times (6 \times 10)}{928 - (3 + 7)} := \frac{(5 + (4 - 6)) \times 10}{(9 + 2) \times 8 - 37} := \frac{5 \times (4 - (6 - 10))}{((9 + (2 \times 8)) \times 3) - 7} := \frac{5 \times (4 + (6 \times (1 - 0)))}{(9^2) + (8 + (3 - 7))} \\ &:= \frac{((5 - 4)^6) \times 10}{9 + (2 \times (8 + (3 - 7)))} := \frac{5 + (4 + (61 - 0))}{(9 - 2) \times ((8 \times 3) - 7)} := \frac{(5 \times (4 \times 6)) - 10}{(9 + 2) \times ((8 \times 3) - 7)} := \frac{5 \times (4 \times (6 + (1 - 0)))}{(9 + (28 - 3)) \times 7} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + (4 + 6)) \times 10}{9 + ((2^8) - (3 + 7))} := \frac{5 \times ((4 \times 6) + 10)}{9 + (28 \times (3 + 7))} := \frac{5 \times (46 - 10)}{9 \times (2 - (8 \times (3 - 7)))} := \frac{5 \times (46 + 10)}{(92 - (8 \times 3)) \times 7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{69102}{75384} &:= \frac{6 + (9 \times (1 - (0 - 2)))}{7 - (5 - (38 - 4))} := \frac{6 + ((9 + 10) \times 2)}{7 + (5 + (3 \times (8 + 4)))} := \frac{(6 \times 9) - (1 + (0 - 2))}{(7 - (5 - 3)) \times (8 + 4)} := \frac{691 - (0 - 2)}{(7 + (5 - 3)) \times 84} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (9 - (1 \times (0 - 2)))}{7 + (53 + (8 + 4))} := \frac{69 + (10 - 2)}{7 \times (5 + (3 + (8 - 4)))} := \frac{((6 \times 9) - 10) \times 2}{((7 - 5)^3) \times (8 + 4)} := \frac{6 - (9 - 102)}{7 + (5 + (3 \times (8 \times 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{((6 \times 9) + (1 - 0)) \times 2}{7 + ((5^3) - (8 + 4))} := \frac{6 + ((9 - (1 - 0)) \times 2)}{7 + (5 + (3 \times (8 - 4)))} := \frac{(6 \times 9) + (10^2)}{7 \times ((5 - 3) \times (8 + 4))} := \frac{((6 \times 9) + (1 - 0))^2}{75 \times ((3 + 8) \times 4)} \end{aligned}$$

• **Four Digit's Representations**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1854}{367092} &:= \frac{((1^{85}) \times 4)}{((3^6) + (70 - (9 - 2)))} := \frac{((1 + (8 - 5)) \times 4)}{(36 \times (7 - (0 - (9^2))))} := \frac{((18 \times 5) - 4)}{(3 \times (6 + (70 \times (9^2))))} := \frac{(1 - (8 - (5 \times 4)))}{(3 \times (((6 \times 70) + 9) \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (8 - (5 + 4)))}{(3 \times (6 - (7 \times (0 - (9 \times 2)))))} := \frac{(1 \times ((8 \times 5) - 4))}{(36 + 7092)} := \frac{(1 \times (8 - (5 - 4)))}{(3 \times (6 \times (7 \times (0 + (9 + 2)))))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (5 - 4)))}{(3 \times (6 \times (7 - (0 - (9^2)))))} \\ &:= \frac{1^{854}}{((3 + (6 \times (7 - (0 - 9)))) \times 2)} := \frac{(1 + (8 \times (5 - 4)))}{(3 \times (6 \times (7 - (0 - 92))))} := \frac{(1 + (8 + (5 + 4)))}{(36 \times (7 - (0 - 92)))} := \frac{(18 + (5 - 4))}{(3670 + 92)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{2397}{105468} &:= \frac{((2 \times (3 + 9)) + 7)}{(((1 - (0 - 5))^4) + 68)} := \frac{((2 \times (3 + 9)) - 7)}{((10 + (5 - 4)) \times 68)} := \frac{((2 \times 3) - (9 - 7))}{((1 + (0 - 5)) \times (4 - (6 \times 8)))} := \frac{((2 \times 39) + 7)}{((1 - (0 - 54)) \times 68)} \\ &:= \frac{((2^3) + (9 + 7))}{(1054 - (6 - 8))} := \frac{(2 - (3 - (9 - 7)))}{(1 - (0 - (5 + (46 - 8))))} := \frac{(2 \times (3 \times (9 - 7)))}{((10 + (5 - 4)) \times (6 \times 8))} := \frac{(2 \times (3 + (9 - 7)))}{((1 - (0 - ((5 + 4) \times 6))) \times 8)} \\ &:= \frac{(2^{3-9+7})}{((1 + (0 - (5 \times (4 - 6)))) \times 8)} := \frac{(2 + ((3 \times 9) - 7))}{((1 - (0 - (5 \times (4 \times 6)))) \times 8)} := \frac{(2 + (3 - (9 - 7)))}{(10 + (54 + 68))} := \frac{(2 + (3 \times (9 - 7)))}{((105 \times 4) - 68)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{2538}{164970} &:= \frac{(((2 \times 5)^3) + 8)}{((16^4) - (9 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{((2 \times 53) - 8)}{((1 + ((6 + 4) \times 9)) \times 70)} := \frac{((2^5) + (3 \times 8))}{((16 + (4 \times 9)) \times 70)} := \frac{((2^5) + 38)}{((1 + 649) \times (7 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{((2 - 5) \times (3 - 8))}{((1^6) + (4 + 970))} := \frac{((25 + 3) \times 8)}{(16 \times ((4 + 9) \times 70))} := \frac{(2 - (5 - (3 + 8)))}{(1 + (((6 - 4)^9) + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(2 - (5 + (3 - 8)))}{((1 + 64) \times (9 - (7 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times ((5 \times 3) - 8))}{((1^6) \times ((4 + 9) \times 70))} := \frac{(2 + (53 + 8))}{((1 + 64) \times (9 \times (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(25 - (3 \times 8))}{(1 \times (6 - (4 - (9 \times (7 - 0)))))} := \frac{(25 + (3 + 8))}{(((1 + 6)^4) + (9 - 70))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{2793}{156408} &:= \frac{((2 - (7 - 9)) \times 3)}{(1 \times (56 \times (4 - (0 - 8))))} := \frac{((2 \times (7 + 9)) + 3)}{(1 \times ((5 + (6 \times 40)) \times 8))} := \frac{(2 - ((7 - 9) \times 3))}{(1 \times (((5 + 6) \times 40) + 8))} := \frac{(2 - (7 - (9 \times 3)))}{(((1 + (5 \times 6)) \times 40) - 8)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (7 - (9 + 3)))}{((1 - (5 \times (6 + 4))) \times (0 - 8))} := \frac{(2 - (7 - (9 - 3)))}{(1 \times ((5 + (6 - (4 - 0))) \times 8))} := \frac{(2 \times ((7 \times 9) - 3))}{((15 + 6) \times (40 \times 8))} := \frac{(2 \times ((7 + 9)^3))}{(((1^5) + 6) \times (4^{08}))} \\ &:= \frac{(2^{7-9+3})}{(1 \times ((5 \times (6 \times (4 - 0))) - 8))} := \frac{(2 + (7 - (9 - 3)))}{(156 + (4 - (0 - 8)))} := \frac{(2 + (7 + (9 - 3)))}{(15 \times (64 + (0 - 8)))} := \frac{(27 + (9 - 3))}{((1 + (5 \times (6 + 40))) \times 8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{3294}{175680} &:= \frac{((3^2) \times (9 \times 4))}{((1 + (7 \times 5)) \times (6 \times 80))} := \frac{((3^2) \times (9 + 4))}{((1 + (7 \times (5 + 6))) \times 80)} := \frac{((3 + (2 \times 9)) \times 4)}{((1^7) \times (56 \times 80))} := \frac{(3 - (2 - (9 - 4)))}{(((1 + 7) \times (5 \times 6)) + 80)} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times ((2 \times 9) - 4))}{((17 + (5 + 6)) \times 80)} := \frac{(3 \times ((2 + 9) \times 4))}{((1 + 7) \times ((5 + 6) \times 80))} := \frac{(3 \times (2^{9-4}))}{((1 + (7 + 56)) \times 80)} := \frac{(3 \times (2 + (9 + 4)))}{((1 + ((7 \times 5) - 6)) \times 80)} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (2 \times (9 \times 4)))}{((1 - (7 - 56)) \times 80)} := \frac{(3 + (2 + (9 + 4)))}{(1 \times ((7 - 5) \times (6 \times 80)))} := \frac{(3 + (29 + 4))}{((1 - (7 - (5 \times 6))) \times 80)} := \frac{(32 - (9 - 4))}{(1 \times ((7 + (5 + 6)) \times 80))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{3297}{461580} &:= \frac{(((3 - 2)^9) + 7)}{((4 + (6 - (1 - 5))) \times 80)} := \frac{((3 \times (2 + 9)) + 7)}{((4 + (61 + 5)) \times 80)} := \frac{((3 \times 2) - (9 - 7))}{((4 + (61 + 5)) \times (8 - 0))} := \frac{((3 \times 2)^{9-7})}{(((4^{6-1}) \times 5) - 80)} \\ &:= \frac{((3 \times 29) - 7)}{(4 \times ((6 + 1) \times (5 \times 80)))} := \frac{(((3^2) + (9 - 7))}{(4 \times ((61 \times 5) + 80))} := \frac{((3 - 2) \times (9 - 7))}{((4 \times (6 \times 15)) - 80)} := \frac{((3 - 2)^{9-7})}{(4 + (61 - (5 - 80)))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 - (2 - (9 + 7)))}{((4 \times 615) - 80)} := \frac{(3 - (2 - (9 - 7)))}{(4 \times (((6 - 1) \times 5) + 80))} := \frac{(32 - (9 + 7))}{(4 \times ((6 + (1^5)) \times 80))} := \frac{(32 + (9 + 7))}{(4 \times ((6 + 15) \times 80))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4086}{132795} &:= \frac{((4 - (0 - 8)) \times 6)}{(13 \times ((27 + 9) \times 5))} := \frac{((4 \times (0 + 8)) + 6)}{((1 + (3 + (27 \times 9))) \times 5)} := \frac{(4 - ((0 \times 8) - 6))}{((1 + (3 - (2 - (7 \times 9)))) \times 5)} := \frac{(4 - (0 - (8 + 6)))}{(((1 - (3 - ((2^7) - 9))) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - (0 - (8 - 6)))}{(1 \times ((3 + (27 + 9)) \times 5))} := \frac{(4 - (0 \times 86))}{(1 - (3 - ((2^7) + (9 - 5))))} := \frac{(4 \times ((0 \times 8) + 6))}{((1 - (3 - (2 \times 79))) \times 5)} := \frac{(4 \times (0 + (8 - 6)))}{((1 + ((3 \times (2 \times 7)) + 9)) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (0 + 86))}{((1 + 3) \times 2795)} := \frac{(4^{08-6})}{(1 + (3 \times ((2^7) + (9 \times 5))))} := \frac{(4 + (0 - (8 - 6)))}{((1 + (3 \times (2 - (7 - 9)))) \times 5)} := \frac{(40 + (8 + 6))}{(1 \times ((32 + 7) \times (9 \times 5)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4326}{105987} &:= \frac{(((4 + 3) \times 2) + 6)}{(10 + (5 \times (9 + 87)))} := \frac{(((4 - 3)^2) \times 6)}{(1 - (0 - (59 + 87)))} := \frac{((4 - (3 - 2)) \times 6)}{((10 + ((5 \times 9) + 8)) \times 7)} := \frac{((4 \times (3 + 2)) - 6)}{(((10 \times 5) - (9 - 8)) \times 7)} \\ &:= \frac{((4 - 3) \times (2 + 6))}{((10 \times (5 + 9)) + (8 \times 7))} := \frac{(4 \times ((3^2) - 6))}{((10 - ((5 - 9) \times 8)) \times 7)} := \frac{(4 \times (3 - (2 - 6)))}{((1^{05}) \times (98 \times 7))} := \frac{(4^{(3-2)^6})}{(((10 + (5 - (9 - 8))) \times 7)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + ((3^2) \times 6))}{((105 + 98) \times 7)} := \frac{(4 + ((3 + 2) \times 6))}{((10 \times 5) + (9 \times 87))} := \frac{(4 + ((3 - 2) \times 6))}{(10 - (5 \times (9 - (8 \times 7))))} := \frac{(4 + (32 - 6))}{(105 \times ((9 - 8) \times 7))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4769}{381520} &:= \frac{(((4 + 7) \times 6) - 9)}{(3 \times ((81 - 5) \times 20))} := \frac{((4 \times 7) + (6 \times 9))}{((3^8) - (15^{20}))} := \frac{((4 + (7 - 6)) \times 9)}{(((3 + (8 + 1)) \times 5)^2 + 0)} := \frac{((4 - 7) \times (6 - 9))}{(3 \times (8 \times (15 \times (2 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - ((7 - 6)^9))}{(3 \times (8 \times (1 \times (5 \times (2 - 0)))))} := \frac{(4 - (7 - (6 + 9)))}{((3 + ((8 + 1) \times 5)) \times 20)} := \frac{(4 \times ((7 - 6) \times 9))}{(3 \times (8 \times ((1 + 5) \times 20)))} := \frac{(4^{(7-6)^9})}{((3 + (8 + (1 \times 5))) \times 20)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + ((7 - 6)^9))}{(((3 + 81) \times 5) - 20)} := \frac{(4 + (7 + (6 \times 9)))}{((3 + (8 - 1)) \times 520)} := \frac{(4 + (7 + (6 - 9)))}{(((3 \times (8 + 1)) + 5) \times 20)} := \frac{(47 + (6 + 9))}{(((3 \times 81) + 5) \times 20)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{5048}{312976} &:= \frac{((5 \times (0 + 4)) - 8)}{(((3 \times (1 + 2)) + 97) \times 6)} := \frac{((5 + (0 - 4)) \times 8)}{(31 \times (2 \times (9 - (7 - 6))))} := \frac{((50 \times 4) - 8)}{((3 + 1) \times 2976)} := \frac{(5 - ((0 \times 4) - 8))}{(31 \times ((2 \times (9 + 7)) - 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 - (0 - (4 - 8)))}{(3 + (1 \times (2 + ((9 \times 7) - 6))))} := \frac{(5 - (0 \times 48))}{(31 \times (2 + (9 - (7 - 6))))} := \frac{(5 \times (0 + (4 + 8)))}{(31 \times ((2 \times (9 \times 7)) - 6))} := \frac{(5 + (0 - (4 - 8)))}{(3 + (1 + ((2^9) + (7 \times 6))))} \\ &:= \frac{(50 - (4 \times 8))}{(3 \times ((1 - (2 - (9 \times 7))) \times 6))} := \frac{(50 - (4 + 8))}{((3 - (1 - 29)) \times 76)} := \frac{(50 - (4 - 8))}{(31 \times ((2 + (9 + 7)) \times 6))} := \frac{(50 - 48)}{(3 + (1 + ((2 \times (9 \times 7)) - 6)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{5091}{437826} & := \frac{(5 - ((0 \times 9) - 1))}{(4 \times (3 - (7 \times (8 - 26))))} := \frac{(5 - (0 - (9 \times 1)))}{(43 \times (7 \times (8 + (2 - 6))))} := \frac{(5 - (0 - (9 + 1)))}{((4 \times ((3 + (7 + 8))^2) - 6)} := \frac{(5 - (0 \times 91))}{(4 + (3 \times (78 + (2^6))))} \\ & := \frac{(5 - (0 - 91))}{((4 \times (3^7)) - (82 \times 6))} := \frac{(5 \times (0 + (9 \times 1)))}{(43 \times (78 + (2 \times 6)))} := \frac{(5 + ((0 \times 9) - 1))}{(4 \times (3 + (7 + (82 - 6))))} := \frac{(50 - (9 \times 1))}{(43 \times (78 - (2 - 6)))} \\ & := \frac{(50 - (9 - 1))}{(43 \times (7 \times (8 - (2 - 6))))} := \frac{(50 + (9 \times 1))}{(43 \times ((7 \times (8 \times 2)) + 6))} := \frac{(50 + (9 + 1))}{(43 \times ((7 + 8) \times (2 + 6))} := \frac{(50 + (9 - 1))}{(((4^3) \times 78) + (2 - 6))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5237}{418960} & := \frac{(((5 + 2)^3) - 7)}{((4 - 1) \times 8960)} := \frac{((5 \times (2 + 3)) + 7)}{((4 + 1) \times (8^{9-6} + 0))} := \frac{(((5 \times (2 + 3)) - 7)}{((41 - (8 + 9)) \times 60)} := \frac{(((5 \times (2 - 3)) + 7)}{(4 + ((18 \times 9) - (6 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{(5 - ((2 - 3) \times 7))}{((4 \times (1 - (8 - 9))) \times 60)} := \frac{(5 \times (2 - (3 - 7)))}{(4 \times (((1^8) + 9) \times 60))} := \frac{(5 \times (2 + (3 + 7)))}{((4 + (1^8)) \times 960)} := \frac{(5 + ((2^3) - 7))}{(4 \times (1 \times (8 \times (9 + (6 - 0))))} \\ & := \frac{(5 + (2 + (3 - 7)))}{(4 \times (1 + (8 - (9 - 60))))} := \frac{(52 - (3 - 7))}{((4 + 1) \times (896 - 0))} := \frac{(52 + (3 - 7))}{(4 \times ((1^8) \times 960))} := \frac{(52 - 37)}{((4 - (1 - (8 + 9))) \times 60)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5472}{103968} & := \frac{(((5 - 4)^7) \times 2)}{(1 - (0 - ((3 \times (9 + 6)) - 8)))} := \frac{(((5 - 4)^7) + 2)}{(1 + (0 - (3 + (9 - 68))))} := \frac{((5 \times (4 + 7)) - 2)}{((10^3) + (9 + (6 - 8)))} := \frac{((5 - 4) \times (7 + 2))}{(1 \times (0 + (3 \times (9 + (6 \times 8))))} \\ & := \frac{((5 - 4)^{7-2})}{(1 \times (0 + ((3^{9-6}) - 8)))} := \frac{(5 - (4 - (7^2)))}{(10 \times ((3 \times 9) + 68))} := \frac{(5 - (4 - (7 + 2)))}{(10 \times ((3^{9-6}) - 8))} := \frac{(5 - (4 - (7 - 2)))}{(103 + (9 - (6 - 8)))} \\ & := \frac{(5 \times (4 + (7 \times 2)))}{(10 \times (3 \times (9 + (6 \times 8))))} := \frac{(5 + (4 - (7 - 2)))}{((1 + (0 - 39)) \times (6 - 8))} := \frac{(5 + (4 + (7 + 2)))}{((10 \times 39) - (6 \times 8))} := \frac{(54 - (7^2))}{(1 \times (0 + ((3 \times 9) + 68)))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5829}{134067} & := \frac{(((5 - 8) \times 2) + 9)}{(1 - (3 - (4 - (0 - 67))))} := \frac{(((5 \times (8 \times 2)) + 9)}{(1 \times ((340 \times 6) + 7))} := \frac{(((5 \times 8) - 29)}{(((1^3) + 40) \times 6) + 7)} := \frac{(5 - (8 - (2 + 9)))}{((1 + 3) \times (4 - (0 - (6 \times 7))))} \\ & := \frac{(5 - (8 + (2 - 9)))}{(1 + ((3 + (4 - (0 - 6))) \times 7))} := \frac{(5 - (8 - 29))}{(13 \times (4 - (0 - (6 \times 7))))} := \frac{(5 \times ((8 \times 2) - 9))}{(1 - (3 \times (4 \times (0 - 67))))} := \frac{(5^{8+2-9})}{(1 - (3 \times (4 + (0 - (6 \times 7))))} \\ & := \frac{(5 + (8 - (2 + 9)))}{(((1^3) \times (4 - (0 - (6 \times 7))))} := \frac{(5 + (8 + (2 \times 9)))}{(1 \times ((3 \times (40 \times 6)) - 7))} := \frac{(5 + (8 + (2 - 9)))}{(1 \times (3 \times (4 - (0 - (6 \times 7))))} := \frac{(5 + (8 + 29))}{(1 \times (3 \times ((40 + 6) \times 7))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{5967}{310284} & := \frac{(((5 \times 9) - 6) \times 7)}{(((3 + 10)^2) \times 84)} := \frac{(((5 \times (9 - 6)) + 7)}{(((3 \times 10) + (2^8)) \times 4)} := \frac{(((5 \times (9 - 6)) - 7)}{((3 + 10) \times (28 + 4))} := \frac{(((5 \times 9) - (6 \times 7))}{(3 \times ((10 \times 2) + (8 \times 4)))} \\ & := \frac{((5 - 9) \times (6 - 7))}{(((3 \times (10 \times 2)) - 8) \times 4)} := \frac{(5 - (9 - (6 + 7)))}{(3 \times ((10 \times (2 \times 8)) - 4))} := \frac{(5 - (9 - 67))}{((3 + (102 \times 8)) \times 4)} := \frac{(5 + ((9 - 6) \times 7))}{((310 + 28) \times 4)} \\ & := \frac{(5 + (9 - (6 + 7)))}{((3 - (1 \times (0 - (2 + 8)))) \times 4)} := \frac{(5 + (9 - (6 - 7)))}{(3 \times (1 \times (0 + ((2^8) + 4))))} := \frac{(5 + (9 + (6 - 7)))}{(((3 + 10)^2) \times (8 - 4))} := \frac{(59 + (6 + 7))}{((310 + 2) \times (8 + 4))} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{6408}{153792} & := \frac{((6 - (4 - 0)) \times 8)}{(1 + (5 + (3 \times (7 \times (9 \times 2))))} := \frac{((6 \times (4 - 0)) + 8)}{(1 \times ((5 + 379) \times 2))} := \frac{(6 - (4 \times (0 \times 8)))}{((1 - (5 + (3 - 79))) \times 2)} := \frac{(6 - (4 + (0 - 8)))}{(1 \times (5 + ((3 \times 79) - 2)))} \\ & := \frac{(6 \times (4 - (0 \times 8)))}{(1 + (5 + (3 + (7 \times (9^2))))} := \frac{(6 \times (4 - (0 - 8)))}{((1 + 53) \times ((7 + 9) \times 2))} := \frac{(6 \times (4 \times (0 + 8)))}{((15 + 3) \times ((7 + 9)^2))} := \frac{(6 \times (40 + 8))}{(((1 + 5)^3) \times ((7 + 9) \times 2))} \\ & := \frac{(6 + (4 - (0 - 8)))}{((153 + (7 \times 9)) \times 2)} := \frac{(6 + (4 + (0 - 8)))}{(1 + (5 + (3 \times (7 + (9 - 2))))} := \frac{(6 + (40 + 8))}{(1 + (5 \times (3 + ((7 + 9)^2))))} := \frac{(640 + 8)}{(((1 + 5)^{3-7+9}) \times 2)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{7014}{329658} & := \frac{((7 - (0 - 1)) \times 4)}{(32 \times (9 + ((6 \times 5) + 8)))} := \frac{(7 - (0 - (1 \times 4)))}{((3 \times ((29 + 6) \times 5)) - 8)} := \frac{(7 - (0 - (1^4)))}{((32 + ((9 - 6) \times 5)) \times 8)} := \frac{(7 - (0 - (1 + 4)))}{(3 \times (2 \times ((9 \times 6) + (5 \times 8))))} \\ & := \frac{(7 - (0 - (1 - 4)))}{((3 \times ((2 \times 9) - 6) \times 5) + 8)} := \frac{(7 - (0 \times 14))}{(329^{(6-5)^8})} := \frac{(7 - (0 - 14))}{(329 \times (6 + (5 - 8)))} := \frac{(7 + (0 - (1 \times 4)))}{(3 - (2 \times (9 - (6 \times (5 + 8))))} \\ & := \frac{(7 + (0 - (1^4)))}{(3 \times (2 \times (9 + ((6 \times 5) + 8))))} := \frac{(7 + (0 - (1 + 4)))}{(3 - (2 - (96 + (5 - 8))))} := \frac{(7 + (0 - (1 - 4)))}{((3 + 2) \times ((9 \times 6) + (5 \times 8)))} := \frac{(70 - 14)}{(((3 \times (2 \times (9 \times 6))) + 5) \times 8)} \\ \blacktriangleright \frac{7459}{126803} & := \frac{(((7 - 4) \times 5) + 9)}{(1 \times (2 \times (68 \times (0 + 3))))} := \frac{(((7 - 4) \times 5) - 9)}{(1 \times (2 \times ((6 \times (8 - 0)) + 3)))} := \frac{(((7 \times (4 - 5)) + 9)}{(1 \times (2 \times (6 + (8 - (0 - 3))))} := \frac{(((7 \times 4) + (5 \times 9))}{(((1 + 2)^6) + (8^{03}))} \\ & := \frac{((7 + (4 + 5)) \times 9)}{(12 \times (68 \times (0 + 3)))} := \frac{(7 - ((4 - 5) \times 9))}{(1 + (268 - (0 - 3)))} := \frac{(7 - (4 - (5 \times 9)))}{(1 + ((2 \times 6) + 803))} := \frac{(7 - (4 - (5 + 9)))}{(1 - (2 \times (6 \times (8 \times (0 - 3))))} \\ & := \frac{(7 + ((4 \times 5) + 9))}{(12 \times ((6 \times (8 - 0)) + 3))} := \frac{(7 + (4 - (5 - 9)))}{((1 - (2 - (6 + 80))) \times 3)} := \frac{(7 + (45 + 9))}{(1 + (2 \times (6 + (8^{03}))))} := \frac{(74 - (5 \times 9))}{(1 + (2 \times (6 + (80 \times 3))))} \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{7614}{209385} := \frac{(7 \times 6) - 14}{(2 \times ((0 \times 9) + 385))} := \frac{((7 + (6 - 1)) \times 4)}{((2 - (0 - 9)) \times (3 \times (8 \times 5)))} := \frac{(7 - (6 - (1^4)))}{(2 - (0 - (93 - (8 \times 5))))} := \frac{(7 - (6 - (1 + 4)))}{((2 \times (0 + (93 - 8))) - 5)}$

$:= \frac{(7 - (6 + (1 - 4)))}{((2 - (0 - (9 + (3 + 8)))) \times 5)} := \frac{(7 \times (6 + (1 \times 4)))}{((20 \times ((9 + 3) \times 8)) + 5)} := \frac{(7 + (6 - (1^4)))}{(2 \times (0 + ((9 + (3 \times 8)) \times 5)))} := \frac{(7 + (6 + (1^4)))}{((2 \times (0 \times 9)) + 385)}$

$:= \frac{(7 + (6 + (1 - 4)))}{((20 \times (9 - (3 - 8))) - 5)} := \frac{(76 \times 14)}{((20 + ((9^3) \times 8)) \times 5)} := \frac{(76 \times (1^4))}{((2 - (0 - 9)) \times (38 \times 5))} := \frac{(76 - 14)}{((20 \times (93 - 8)) + 5)}$

► $\frac{7641}{290358} := \frac{(((7 - 6)^4) + 1)}{(2 \times (((9 + (0 - 3)) \times 5) + 8))} := \frac{((7 \times (6 - 4)) + 1)}{((2^{9+0 \times 3}) + 58)} := \frac{((7 \times 6) + (4 \times 1))}{((2 \times 903) - 58)} := \frac{(((7^6 - 4) - 1))}{((2 \times (903 + 5)) + 8)}$

$:= \frac{((7 - 6) \times (4 - 1))}{(2 + ((9 - ((0 \times 3) - 5)) \times 8))} := \frac{((7 - 6)^{4 \times 1})}{(2 \times (9 + (0 - (3 - (5 + 8))))))} := \frac{(7 - (6 - (4 \times 1)))}{(2 - ((90 \times (3 - 5)) - 8))} := \frac{(7 - (6 - (4 + 1)))}{(2 - (9 + (0 - ((3^5) - 8))))}$

$:= \frac{(7 - (6 - (4 - 1)))}{((2 + (9 - (0 - (3 + 5)))) \times 8)} := \frac{(7^{6-4-1})}{(2 + (90 + (3 \times 58)))} := \frac{(7 + (6 - (4 + 1)))}{(((2 + (9 - 0)) \times 3) + 5) \times 8)} := \frac{(7 + (6 + (4 \times 1)))}{(2 \times ((9 \times (0 + 35)) + 8))}$

► $\frac{7653}{290814} := \frac{((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 3)}{(((2 \times 90) - (8 + 1)) \times 4)} := \frac{((7 \times 6) + 53)}{((2 + (90 \times 8)) \times (1 + 4))} := \frac{((7 - 6) \times (5 - 3))}{((2 + (9 - (0 - (8 \times 1)))) \times 4)} := \frac{(((7 - 6)^{5-3}))}{(2 - (9 \times (0 - (8 - (1 \times 4))))))}$

$:= \frac{(7 - ((6 - 5) \times 3))}{(2 \times ((9 \times (0 + (8 \times 1))) + 4))} := \frac{(7 - ((6 - 5)^3))}{(2 \times (90 - (8 \times (1 - 4))))} := \frac{(7 - (6 - (5 + 3)))}{((2 \times (9 - 0)) + (81 \times 4))} := \frac{(7 - (6 - (5 - 3)))}{(2 + (90 + (8 + 14)))}$

$:= \frac{(7 - (6 - 53))}{(((2^{9+0 \times 8}) + 1) \times 4)} := \frac{(7^{(6-5)^3})}{((2 + (9 - (0 - 8))) \times 14)} := \frac{(7 + (6 - (5 + 3)))}{(2 \times (90 + (8 + (1 - 4))))} := \frac{(7 + (6 \times (5 - 3)))}{(2 + (90 \times (8 \times (1^4))))}$

► $\frac{7682}{130594} := \frac{(((7 - 6)^8) \times 2)}{(1 \times (3 + (0 - (5 - (9 \times 4))))))} := \frac{((7 \times 6) - (8 + 2))}{((1 - (3 \times (0 - (5 \times 9)))) \times 4)} := \frac{((7 + (6 - 8))^2)}{(1 + ((30 \times (5 + 9)) + 4))} := \frac{((7 - 6) \times (8 - 2))}{(1 \times (3 - (0 - (5 + 94))))}$

$:= \frac{((7 - 6)^{8-2})}{(1 + ((3 \times (0 - (5 - 9))) + 4))} := \frac{(7 - (6 - (8 \times 2)))}{(1 + ((3 - (0 - 5)) \times (9 \times 4)))} := \frac{(7 - (6 - (8 + 2)))}{(1 + ((30 \times 5) + (9 \times 4))} := \frac{(7 - (6 - (8 - 2)))}{(1 \times (30 - (5 - 94)))}$

$:= \frac{(7 - (6 - 82))}{(1 - (3 \times (0 - (5 \times 94))))} := \frac{(7 + ((6 \times 8) - 2))}{(1 + ((30 - 5) \times (9 \times 4)))} := \frac{(7 + ((6 + 8) \times 2))}{((1^3 + 0) + 594)} := \frac{(7 + (6 - (8 + 2)))}{(1 \times ((3 \times (0 + 5)) + (9 \times 4)))}$

► $\frac{8092}{137564} := \frac{((8 \times (0 \times 9)) + 2)}{(1 - (3 - (7 + (5 + (6 \times 4))))))} := \frac{((8 \times (0 + 9)) + 2)}{(1 \times (37 \times ((5 \times 6) + 4))} := \frac{(8 - ((0 \times 9) - 2))}{(1 + ((3 \times (7 \times 5)) + 64))} := \frac{(8 - (0 - (9 \times 2)))}{(((1 - (3 - 75)) \times 6) + 4)}$

$:= \frac{(8 - (0 - (9 - 2)))}{(1 \times (3 + ((7 + 56) \times 4))} := \frac{(8 - (0 \times 92))}{(1 \times (3 - (7 \times (5 - (6 \times 4))))))} := \frac{(8 \times ((0 \times 9) + 2))}{((1 + (3 + ((7 - 5)^6))) \times 4)} := \frac{(8 \times (0 + (9 - 2)))}{((1 + 3) \times (7 \times ((5 \times 6) + 4)))}$

$:= \frac{(8^{0 \times 9 + 2})}{((1 + ((3 \times 7) - 5)) \times 64)} := \frac{(8 + ((0 \times 9) - 2))}{(1 \times (3 + (75 + (6 \times 4))))} := \frac{(8 + (0 - (9 - 2)))}{(1 \times (3 + (7 + (5 + (6 - 4)))))} := \frac{(80 - (9 + 2))}{(1 + ((3 \times (7 \times 56)) - 4))}$

► $\frac{8219}{435607} := \frac{((8 - 2) \times (1 + 9))}{(4 \times (3 \times (5 \times (60 - 7))))} := \frac{(8 - (2 - (1^9)))}{((4^3) + ((5 \times 60) + 7))} := \frac{(8 - (2 \times (1^9)))}{(((4 - (3 - 5)) \times (60 - 7))} := \frac{(8 - (2 + (1^9)))}{(((4 \times (3 + (5 + 60))) - 7)}$

$:= \frac{(8 + ((2 + 1) \times 9))}{(((4 + 3) \times (5 \times (60 - 7))))} := \frac{(8 + ((2 - 1) \times 9))}{(((4 \times 3) + 5) \times (60 - 7))} := \frac{(8 + (2 - (1 \times 9)))}{(((4^3) - (5 + (6 - (0 \times 7))))} := \frac{(8 + (2 - (1^9)))}{(4 + (((3 + 5) \times 60) - 7))}$

$:= \frac{(8 + (2 \times (1 + 9)))}{(4 \times ((3 - 56) \times (0 - 7)))} := \frac{(8 + (2 + (1 \times 9)))}{((4 + (3 \times 5)) \times (60 - 7))} := \frac{(8 + (2 + (1 - 9)))}{(4 + (35 + (60 + 7)))} := \frac{(8 + (21 + 9))}{(((43 - 5) \times (60 - 7))}$

► $\frac{8357}{142069} := \frac{(((8 - 3) \times 5) - 7)}{(((14 \times (2 - 0)) + 6) \times 9)} := \frac{(8 - (3 - (5 + 7)))}{(1 + (4 \times ((2 - (0 - 6)) \times 9)))} := \frac{(8 - (3 - (5 - 7)))}{(((1 + (4 + (2 - 0))) \times 6) + 9)} := \frac{(8 - (3 \times (5 - 7)))}{(1 \times (4 + ((20 + 6) \times 9)))}$

$:= \frac{(8^{3+5-7})}{(1 + (((4 + 20) \times 6) - 9))} := \frac{(8 + ((3 \times 5) + 7))}{(((14 + 20) \times (6 + 9))} := \frac{(8 + (3 - (5 - 7)))}{(1 + (4 \times ((2^0)^6 - 9)))} := \frac{(8 + (3 \times (5 - 7)))}{(1 \times (4 - (2 \times (0 - (6 + 9))))))}$

$:= \frac{(8 + (3 + (5 - 7)))}{((1 - (4 \times (2 + (0 - 6)))) \times 9)} := \frac{(8 + (35 - 7))}{(1 \times ((4 + (2^0)^6)) \times 9)} := \frac{(83 - (5 \times 7))}{(1 + ((4 \times 206) - 9))} := \frac{(83 + (5 - 7))}{(1 - (4 - (20 \times 69)))}$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8937}{402165} &:= \frac{((8-(9-3)) \times 7)}{(((40 \times (2+1)) + 6) \times 5)} := \frac{((8 \times 9) - 37)}{((40^2) + ((1-6) \times 5))} := \frac{((8-9) \times (3-7))}{((4-(0-(2 \times 16))) \times 5)} := \frac{(8-(9-(3+7)))}{(((40 \times 2) + (1^6)) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(8-(9 \times (3-7)))}{((402-(1 \times 6)) \times 5)} := \frac{(8-(9+(3-7)))}{(4-(0-((21 \times 6) + 5)))} := \frac{(8 \times (9+(3-7)))}{(40 \times ((2+(1+6)) \times 5))} := \frac{(8+((9 \times 3)-7))}{((40+(2 \times 1)) \times (6 \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(8+(9-(3+7)))}{((40 \times (2+(1 \times 6))) - 5)} := \frac{(8+(9+(3-7)))}{(((4 \times (0+2)) + 1) \times 65)} := \frac{(8+(9+37))}{(((40 \times 2) + 1) \times (6 \times 5))} := \frac{(8+(93-7))}{(((40 \times 21) + 6) \times 5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8952}{340176} &:= \frac{((8-(9-5)) \times 2)}{(340+((1-7) \times 6))} := \frac{((8 \times (9-5)) - 2)}{(3 \times ((4-(0-1)) \times 76))} := \frac{(8-(9-(5 \times 2)))}{(340+(1+(7-6)))} := \frac{(8-(9-(5^2)))}{(3 \times (4 \times (0+(1 \times 76))))} \\ &:= \frac{(8-(9-(5+2)))}{((3+((4-(0-1)) \times 7)) \times 6)} := \frac{(8-(9-(5-2)))}{(3-(4+(0-(1+76))))} := \frac{(8-(9-52))}{((3+(40 \times (1+7))) \times 6)} := \frac{(8 \times (9-(5+2)))}{((3+(4-(0-1))) \times 76)} \\ &:= \frac{(8+(9-(5 \times 2)))}{((34 \times (0+(1+7))) - 6)} := \frac{(8+(9-(5-2)))}{((3-(4 \times (0-1))) \times 76)} := \frac{(8+(9+(5 \times 2)))}{(3 \times ((40+17) \times 6))} := \frac{(89-(5-2))}{(3+(40 \times 1)) \times 76} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9735}{124608} &:= \frac{(((9 \times 7) - 3) \times 5)}{(1 \times (2 \times (4 \times (60 \times 8))))} := \frac{(((9+7)^3) \times 5)}{(1 \times ((2 \times 4)^{6+0 \times 8}))} := \frac{(((9-7)^3) \times 5)}{((124-60) \times 8)} := \frac{((9 \times (7+3)) - 5)}{(1 \times ((2^4) \times (60+8)))} \\ &:= \frac{((9+(7 \times 3)) \times 5)}{((1^2) \times (4 \times (60 \times 8)))} := \frac{((9-7) \times (3 \times 5))}{(1 \times (2 \times (4 \times (6 \times (0+8))))} := \frac{(9-(7-(3+5)))}{((12 \times (4+(6-0))) + 8)} := \frac{(9 \times ((7+3) \times 5))}{((1+2) \times (4 \times (60 \times 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 \times ((7-3) \times 5))}{(12 \times (4 \times (6 \times (0+8))))} := \frac{(9 \times (7+(3-5)))}{((1+2) \times (4 \times (6 \times (0+8))))} := \frac{(9+((7 \times 3) + 5))}{((1-2) \times ((4-60) \times 8))} := \frac{(9+(7 \times (3+5)))}{(1 \times ((2^4) \times (60-8)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9846}{315072} &:= \frac{(((9+8) \times 4) - 6)}{(31 \times (50+(7 \times 2)))} := \frac{(((9-8)^4) \times 6)}{(3 \times (1 \times (50+(7 \times 2))))} := \frac{(((9-8)^4)^6)}{((3+(1+(5-(0-7)))) \times 2)} := \frac{((9 \times 8) - (4 \times 6))}{((31 \times 50) - (7 \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{((9-8) \times (4+6))}{(((3 \times (1+50)) + 7) \times 2)} := \frac{((9-8) \times 46)}{(((3 \times (1+(5-0))) + 7) \times 2)} := \frac{(9-(8-(4+6)))}{(3+(1+((50 \times 7) - 2)))} := \frac{(9-(8+(4-6)))}{((3+1) \times ((5-(0-7)) \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 \times (8+(4 \times 6)))}{(((3+1)^5 + 0) \times (7+2))} := \frac{(9+((8+4) \times 6))}{((31+(5-0)) \times 72)} := \frac{(9+((8-4) \times 6))}{(3 \times (1 \times ((50 \times 7) + 2)))} := \frac{(9+(8+(4+6)))}{((3-15) \times (0-72))} \end{aligned}$$

3.12 13 Equivalent Blocks

• Five Digit's Numerator

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{12948}{35607} &:= \frac{1-(2-(9+(4-8)))}{3-(5-(6-(0-7)))} := \frac{1-(2-(9-(4-8)))}{3 \times (5+(6-(0 \times 7)))} := \frac{1-(2-(9+(4+8)))}{((3+5) \times (6-0)) + 7} := \frac{1 \times ((2-9) \times (4-8))}{35-(6 \times (0-7))} \\ &:= \frac{1+(2+(9+(4-8)))}{35-(6-(0-7))} := \frac{(1+(2+(9-4))) \times 8}{(3^5)-(60+7)} := \frac{((1+(2 \times 9)) \times 4) + 8}{3 \times ((5+(6-0)) \times 7)} := \frac{1 \times (2+(94-8))}{(3^5)+(6+(0-7))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((2+9) \times (4+8))}{356-(0-7)} := \frac{1+(2+(9+(4+8)))}{3+(56-(0-7))} := \frac{1 \times (2 \times (94-8))}{((3+5) \times 60) - 7} := \frac{1 \times (2^{9+4-8})}{35+(60-7)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (((2^9) \times 4) - 8)}{3+5607} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{15780}{69432} &:= \frac{1+(5+(7-(8-0)))}{6+((9-(4-3)) \times 2)} := \frac{(1^5) \times (7+(8-0))}{6 \times (9-(4-(3 \times 2)))} := \frac{1 \times (5+(7+(8-0)))}{(6 \times ((9-4) \times 3)) - 2} := \frac{(15 \times 7) - 80}{6+((9+43) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{15+(7+(8-0))}{6 \times (9+(4+(3^2)))} := \frac{1 \times (5 \times (7+(8-0)))}{6+(9 \times (4+32))} := \frac{((1^5)^7) \times 80}{(6+(9-4)) \times 32} := \frac{(1+5) \times (7+(8-0))}{6 \times (((9 \times 4) - 3) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{157+(8-0)}{694+32} := \frac{(15+7) \times 80}{(6^9-4) - 32} := \frac{15 \times (7+(8-0))}{(6+9) \times ((4^3) + 2)} := \frac{1 \times (5+780)}{(6 \times (9 \times (4^3))) - 2} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (57+(8-0))}{6+((94 \times 3) - 2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{16805}{73942} &:= \frac{(1+(6-8)) \times (0-5)}{7-(3-(9 \times (4-2)))} := \frac{1+(6+(8+(0-5)))}{(7+(3 \times (9-4))) \times 2} := \frac{1+(6+(8-(0 \times 5)))}{73+(9-(4^2))} := \frac{1+(6+(8-(0-5)))}{7+(39+42)} \\ &:= \frac{(16-(8-0)) \times 5}{((7 \times (3+9))+4) \times 2} := \frac{((1^6)+(8-0)) \times 5}{7+(3+(94 \times 2))} := \frac{(1+(6+(8-0))) \times 5}{((73+9) \times 4)+2} := \frac{(1^6) \times (80+5)}{((7-3) \times 94)-2} \\ &:= \frac{16 \times (8 \times (05))}{((7^3)+9) \times (4 \times 2)} := \frac{1-(6+(8 \times (0-5)))}{7+(3+(9 \times (4^2)))} := \frac{(1+(6 \times (8-0))) \times 5}{7 \times ((39 \times 4)-2)} := \frac{(1+6) \times (8 \times (05))}{7+((39-4)^2)} \\ &:= \frac{(16+80) \times 5}{((7^3)+9) \times (4+2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{17205}{96348} &:= \frac{1+(7+(2+(0-5)))}{((9-6) \times (3 \times 4))-8} := \frac{1 \times (7-(2+(0-5)))}{((9+(6-3)) \times 4)+8} := \frac{1+(7+(2-(0-5)))}{9+(63+(4+8))} := \frac{1+((7 \times (2-0))+5)}{(9+(6+(3-4))) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{(1+(7-(2-0))) \times 5}{(9+((6-3) \times 4)) \times 8} := \frac{1+((7^2+0)-5)}{9 \times (((6+3) \times 4)-8)} := \frac{1+(7 \times (2-(0-5)))}{((9+63) \times 4)-8} := \frac{(1-7) \times (2 \times (0-5))}{(96 \times 3)+48} \\ &:= \frac{(1-(7 \times 2)) \times (0-5)}{((96-3) \times 4)-8} := \frac{1 \times (7 \times (2 \times (05)))}{(9+(6+34)) \times 8} := \frac{(1+7) \times (20-5)}{(9-(6-(3^4))) \times 8} := \frac{(17 \times 20)+5}{(9 \times (6^3))- (4+8)} \\ &:= \frac{(1-72) \times (0-5)}{(9 \times ((6^3)+4))+8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{17568}{32940} &:= \frac{1 \times (7-(5-(6+8)))}{3 \times (2 \times (9-(4-0)))} := \frac{17+(5-(6-8))}{3 \times (2+(9+(4-0)))} := \frac{1-(7-((5 \times 6)+8))}{((3 \times 2)+9) \times (4-0)} := \frac{1+(7+((5+6) \times 8))}{(3+2) \times (9 \times (4-0))} \\ &:= \frac{(1-(7-(5 \times 6))) \times 8}{(3-2) \times (9 \times 40)} := \frac{1 \times ((7 \times 56)-8)}{((3^2)+9) \times 40} := \frac{1 \times ((7+56) \times 8)}{3+(2+940)} := \frac{1 \times (7 \times (56+8))}{(3+(2 \times 9)) \times 40} \\ &:= \frac{(1+7) \times ((5+6) \times 8)}{(1+7) \times ((5+6) \times 8)} := \frac{(17 \times 56)+8}{(3+2) \times (9 \times 40)} := \frac{(1-(7-(5+6))) \times 8}{3+(2 \times (9 \times (4-0)))} := \frac{(1+(7 \times 5)) \times (6 \times 8)}{(3^2) \times (9 \times 40)} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((7+(5 \times 6)) \times 8)}{3+((2^9)+40)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{17658}{29430} &:= \frac{1-(7+(6 \times (5-8)))}{2 \times (9+(4-(3-0)))} := \frac{1+(7-(6-(5+8)))}{(2 \times 9)+(4+(3-0))} := \frac{1 \times (76-58)}{2 \times ((9-4) \times (3-0))} := \frac{1 \times (7 \times (6+(5-8)))}{(2^{9-4})+(3-0)} \\ &:= \frac{((1+(7-6))^5)-8}{(2 \times (9-4))+30} := \frac{1+(7+(6+(5+8)))}{2+(9+(4+30))} := \frac{1-((7-(6+5)) \times 8)}{29-(4-30)} := \frac{1 \times (7-((6-5)^8))}{2+(9-(4-(3-0)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((7 \times 6)+(5-8))}{2+(9 \times (4+(3-0)))} := \frac{1+(7-(6-(5 \times 8)))}{2 \times (9-(4-30))} := \frac{1 \times (7+((6 \times 5)+8))}{2+(9+(4^3+0))} := \frac{1-(7-(6-(5-8)))}{2-(9-(4 \times (3-0)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times ((7+65) \times 8)}{(2^{9-4}) \times 30} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{17685}{94320} &:= \frac{1-(7-(6+(8-5)))}{(9-(4-3)) \times (2-0)} := \frac{1+(7-((6-8) \times 5))}{(9 \times 4)+(3 \times 20)} := \frac{17-(6-(8+5))}{(9 \times (4 \times 3))+20} := \frac{(1+(7+(6-8))) \times 5}{(9-(4-3)) \times 20} \\ &:= \frac{(1^{768})+5}{9+(43-20)} := \frac{1+(7+(6+(8 \times 5)))}{9 \times ((4 \times 3)+20)} := \frac{1 \times (7+((6 \times 8)+5))}{(9+(4+3)) \times 20} := \frac{1+(7+((6+8) \times 5))}{(9+4) \times (32-0)} \\ &:= \frac{17+(6+85)}{9 \times (4+(3 \times 20))} := \frac{176+(8 \times 5)}{9 \times (4 \times (32-0))} := \frac{1-(7-(6 \times (8-5)))}{(9-(4-3))^2+0} := \frac{(17-(6+8))^5}{9 \times ((4 \times 3)^2+0)} \\ &:= \frac{(1+7) \times (6^{8-5})}{9 \times (4^{3+2-0})} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{27054}{69138} &:= \frac{2 + (7 - (0 \times 54))}{6 + (9 + ((1^3) \times 8))} := \frac{2 + (7 - (0 - (5 + 4)))}{(6 \times (9 \times (1^3))) - 8} := \frac{27 - (0 \times 54)}{6 - (9 \times ((1^3) - 8))} := \frac{(2 + (7 - (0 \times 5))) \times 4}{6 + (91 + (3 - 8))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - 7) \times (0 - (5 + 4))}{6 + ((9 \times 13) - 8)} := \frac{2 + (70 + (5 + 4))}{69 + 138} := \frac{(2 + 70) \times (5 + 4)}{69 \times (1 \times (3 \times 8))} := \frac{(2^7 + 0) - (5 \times 4)}{6 \times (9 - (1 - 38))} \\ &:= \frac{270 - 54}{69 \times ((1^3) \times 8)} := \frac{27 \times ((05 + 4))}{69 \times ((1^3) + 8)} := \frac{270 - (5 + 4)}{691 - (3 \times 8)} := \frac{270 \times (5 - 4)}{6 \times (91 + (3 \times 8))} \\ &:= \frac{270 + 54}{69 \times (1 + (3 + 8))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{28476}{91530} &:= \frac{2 + (8 + (4 \times (7 - 6)))}{9 + (1 + (5 + 30))} := \frac{2 + (8 - ((4 - 7) \times 6))}{(9 - (1 + 5)) \times 30} := \frac{2 + ((8 \times (4 + 7)) - 6)}{9 \times ((1^5) \times 30)} := \frac{(2 + (8 + (4 + 7))) \times 6}{9 \times (15 + 30)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (8 \times 4)) + 76}{(9 + (1 + 5)) \times 30} := \frac{2 + (8 \times (4 + (7 - 6)))}{9 + (1 + (5^3 + 0))} := \frac{(2^8) - (4 - (7 \times 6))}{915 + 30} := \frac{(28 \times 4) - (7 \times 6)}{9 + ((1 + 5)^3 + 0)} \\ &:= \frac{28 + 476}{9 \times ((1 + 5) \times 30)} := \frac{2 \times (8 + (47 - 6))}{9 \times (1 \times (5 + 30))} := \frac{((2 \times 84) + 7) \times 6}{(9 + (1 + 5))^3 + 0} := \frac{2 \times (84 \times (7 - 6))}{9 + (1 + 530)} \\ &:= \frac{28 \times (47 + 6)}{9 \times (1 \times 530)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{29670}{41538} &:= \frac{(2 \times 9) - (6 + (7 - 0))}{((4 + (1^5)) \times 3) - 8} := \frac{2 + (9 + (6 - (7 - 0)))}{4 + (1 \times (5 - (3 - 8)))} := \frac{(2^{9-6}) + (7 - 0)}{4 + (1 + (5 + (3 + 8)))} := \frac{2 \times (9 - (6 - (7 - 0)))}{4 - (1 + (5 \times (3 - 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{29 - (6 - (7 - 0))}{4 + ((1^5) \times 38)} := \frac{2 - (9 - (6 \times (7 - 0)))}{4 + (1 \times (53 - 8))} := \frac{2 - (9 - (67 - 0))}{(4 \times 15) + (3 \times 8)} := \frac{2 + (9 - (6 - 70))}{41 + ((5 + 3) \times 8)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (9 \times 6)) + (7 - 0)}{41 + (5 \times (3 \times 8))} := \frac{2 \times (9 + (6 + 70))}{((4 - 1)^5) + (3 - 8)} := \frac{(2 \times 96) - (7 - 0)}{4 - (1 - ((5 - 3)^8))} := \frac{2 + (9 \times (6 \times (7 - 0)))}{4 \times (1 \times ((5^3) + 8))} \\ &:= \frac{(2^9) - (67 - 0)}{(41 \times (5 \times 3)) + 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{37245}{91680} &:= \frac{3 + (7 + (2 - (4 - 5)))}{(9 + (1 - 6)) \times (8 - 0)} := \frac{3 - (7 - ((2 + 4) \times 5))}{(9 \times 16) - 80} := \frac{3 - (7 + (2 - 45))}{9 + (1 + (6 + 80))} := \frac{(3 \times ((7 - 2) \times 4)) + 5}{(9 - (1 + 6)) \times 80} \\ &:= \frac{((3 + 7)^2) - (4 + 5)}{(9 \times 16) + 80} := \frac{3 + (7 + (24 \times 5))}{(9 + (1 - 6)) \times 80} := \frac{3 \times ((7 + (2 + 4)) \times 5)}{(9 + 1) \times (6 \times (8 - 0))} := \frac{(((3 + 7)^2) + 4) \times 5}{(9 + (1 + 6)) \times 80} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (7^2)) \times (4 + 5)}{9 \times (16 \times (8 - 0))} := \frac{3 \times (72 - (4 \times 5))}{(9 - 1) \times (6 \times (8 - 0))} := \frac{3 \times ((7 \times (2^4)) + 5)}{9 \times (16 + 80)} := \frac{3 - (7 \times (2 - (4 + 5)))}{(9 + (1 + 6)) \times (8 - 0)} \\ &:= \frac{(37 + 2) \times 45}{9 \times (1 \times (6 \times 80))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{39204}{81675} &:= \frac{3 + (9 - (2 \times (0 \times 4)))}{8 - (1 - (6 + (7 + 5)))} := \frac{(3 + 9) \times (2 - (0 \times 4))}{8 + (1 + (6 + (7 \times 5)))} := \frac{3 + (9 + (20 + 4))}{(8 + ((1^6) \times 7)) \times 5} := \frac{(3 - 9) \times (2 \times (0 - 4))}{(8 - (1 - (6 + 7))) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(3 - (9 \times 2)) \times (0 - 4)}{8 + ((16 \times 7) + 5)} := \frac{(3 + 9) \times (2 - (0 - 4))}{(8 - (1 \times 6)) \times 75} := \frac{3 + (9^{2+0 \times 4})}{(((8 - 1) \times 6) - 7) \times 5} := \frac{(3 + 9) \times (2 \times (04))}{8 + (16 \times (7 + 5))} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times ((9 + (2 - 0)) \times 4)}{((8 \times (1 \times 6)) + 7) \times 5} := \frac{(3 + 9) \times (2^{04})}{(81 + (6 - 7)) \times 5} := \frac{3 \times (92 - (0 - 4))}{(8 + (16 \times 7)) \times 5} := \frac{((3 \times 9)^2 + 0) \times 4}{(8 + 1) \times 675} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (9 \times (2^{04}))}{(81 - 6) \times (7 + 5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{40392}{87516} &:= \frac{4 - ((0 \times 39) - 2)}{8 + (7 + (5 - (1 + 6)))} := \frac{4 + (0 - (3 - (9 + 2)))}{8 + (7 - (5 - 16))} := \frac{4 - (0 - (3 + (9 + 2)))}{8 + (7 + ((5 - 1) \times 6))} := \frac{(4 \times (03)) + (9 \times 2)}{(8^{7-5}) + (1^6)} \\ &:= \frac{40 + (3 - (9 - 2))}{8 + (7 \times (5 - (1 - 6)))} := \frac{((4 \times (03)) + 9) \times 2}{(8 \times (7 + 5)) + (1 - 6)} := \frac{4 \times (0 - ((3 - 9) \times 2))}{8 \times (7 + (5 + (1^6)))} := \frac{40 + (3 + (9 + 2))}{87 + (5 \times (1 \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - (0 - 3)) \times (9 \times 2)}{(8 \times (7 \times 5)) - (1 + 6)} := \frac{4 \times ((03 \times (9 + 2)))}{(8 \times (7 \times (5 \times 1))) + 6} := \frac{4 \times ((0 - (3 - 9))^2)}{(8 - (7 - 51)) \times 6} := \frac{4 \times ((03 + (9^2)))}{8 \times (75 + 16)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times ((0 \times 3) + 9))^2}{8 \times ((7 \times 51) - 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{41895}{67032} &:= \frac{4 - (1 - (8 + (9 + 5)))}{(6 \times (7 - (0 \times 3))) - 2} := \frac{(4 + (1 - (8 - 9))) \times 5}{6 \times (7 - (0 - (3 - 2)))} := \frac{4 \times ((1^8) + (9 + 5))}{6 \times (7 - (0 - (3^2)))} := \frac{(((4 - 1) \times 8) - 9) \times 5}{6 \times ((7 - (0 - 3)) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (1 - (8 - 9))) \times 5}{(6 \times (7 \times (03))) + 2} := \frac{4 \times (1 + (8 - (9 - 5)))}{(6 + (7 - (0 - 3))) \times 2} := \frac{(4 + 1) \times (8 \times (9 - 5))}{(6 + (7 - (0 - 3)))^2} := \frac{(4 - (1^8)) \times 95}{6 \times (70 + (3 \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times ((1 + (8 + 9)) \times 5)}{(6 \times (7 + (0 - 3)))^2} := \frac{(4 - (1 - (8 \times 9))) \times 5}{6 \times ((7 - (0 - 3))^2)} := \frac{(4 \times ((1^8) + 9)) + 5}{6 \times (7 - (0 - (3 + 2)))} := \frac{4 + (1^{895})}{6 - (7 + (0 - (3^2)))} \\ &:= \frac{4 \times ((1 + 8) \times (9 \times 5))}{(6^{7-03}) \times 2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{49203}{71568} &:= \frac{4 + (9 - (2 - (0 \times 3)))}{7 - (1 + (5 \times (6 - 8)))} := \frac{4 + (9 \times (2 - (0 \times 3)))}{((7 - 1) \times 5) - (6 - 8)} := \frac{4 \times (9 + (2 - (0 \times 3)))}{(7 - (1 \times (5 - 6))) \times 8} := \frac{4 - (9 - (20 \times 3))}{7 + (1 \times (5 + 68))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (9 \times (2 - 0))) \times 3}{7 + (1 + ((5 + 6) \times 8))} := \frac{(4 + (9 + 20)) \times 3}{(7 + (1 \times (5 + 6))) \times 8} := \frac{4 + ((9 \times 20) + 3)}{(((7 + 1) \times 5) - 6) \times 8} := \frac{4 - (9 - 203)}{(7 - (1 - (5 \times 6))) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (9 - (2 - 0))) \times 3}{(7 + (1 \times (5 - 6))) \times 8} := \frac{(4 - (9^2)) \times (0 - 3)}{7 \times (1 \times (56 - 8))} := \frac{(4 - 92) \times (0 - 3)}{(7 \times (1 \times 56)) - 8} := \frac{4 \times ((9 + (2 - 0)) \times 3)}{(((7 - 1) \times 5) - 6) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{4 + ((9^2) + 0) + 3}{(7 + (15 - 6)) \times 8} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{51840}{67392} &:= \frac{(5 + (1 \times 8)) \times 40}{(6 - (7 - (3 \times 9)))^2} := \frac{5 + (1 + (8 - (4 - 0)))}{6 - (7 - (3 + (9 + 2)))} := \frac{5 \times (1 \times (8 - (4 - 0)))}{67 - (39 + 2)} := \frac{5 \times (1 \times (8 + (4 - 0)))}{6 + ((7 - 3) \times (9 \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times (18 - (4 - 0))}{6 + (7 - (3 - (9^2)))} := \frac{(5 \times (1 \times 8)) + 40}{6 + (7 \times (3 + (9 + 2)))} := \frac{5 \times (18 + (4 - 0))}{6 - (7 - ((3 + 9)^2))} := \frac{5 \times (1 \times (8 \times (4 - 0)))}{(67 \times 3) + (9 - 2)} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times ((1 + 8) \times (4 - 0))}{6 \times ((7 \times 3) + (9 \times 2))} := \frac{5 \times (1 \times (8 + 40))}{(6 + 7) \times ((3 + 9) \times 2)} := \frac{(5 + (1 + 8)) \times 40}{6 - (7 - ((3 \times 9)^2))} := \frac{5 \times (18 + 40)}{(6 + 7) \times ((3 \times 9) + 2)} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times (1 \times (84 - 0))}{6 \times (7 + (3 + (9^2)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{52407}{93168} &:= \frac{5 + (2 + (4 - (0 - 7)))}{9 - ((3 \times (1 - 6)) - 8)} := \frac{5 + (2 \times (4 - (0 - 7)))}{9 - (3 \times (1 - (6 + 8)))} := \frac{5 - (2 - (40 - 7))}{(9 \times (3 - (1 - 6))) - 8} := \frac{5 + (2 + (40 + 7))}{(9 + (3 \times (1^6))) \times 8} \\ &:= \frac{((5 - 2)^4 + 0) \times 7}{(9 - 3) \times 168} := \frac{(5 - 2)^{4+0 \times 7}}{9 \times (3 - (1 - (6 + 8)))} := \frac{5 + (2 \times (40 + 7))}{(9 - (3 - 16)) \times 8} := \frac{5 + ((2^4) + 0) \times 7}{(9 \times ((3 + 1) \times 6)) - 8} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + (2 - (4 - 0)))^7}{(9^{3-1}) \times (6 \times 8)} := \frac{5 \times ((2^4) + 0) - 7}{9 + (3 + (1 \times 68))} := \frac{5 + (2 + 407)}{(93 - (1^6)) \times 8} := \frac{(5^2) + 407}{(9 - 3) \times (16 \times 8)} \\ &:= \frac{52 + 407}{(9 + (3 \times 1)) \times 68} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{52974}{61803} &:= \frac{5 + ((2 \times 9) - (7 + 4))}{6 + (1 \times (8 - (0 \times 3)))} := \frac{(5 - 2) \times (9 - (7 - 4))}{(6 + (1^8 + 0)) \times 3} := \frac{5 - (2 - (9 \times (7 - 4)))}{(6 + 1) \times (8 + (0 - 3))} := \frac{(5 + (2^{9-7})) \times 4}{(6 + (1 \times (8 - 0))) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + (2 + 9)) \times (7 - 4)}{61 - (8 + (0 - 3))} := \frac{5 + (2 - (9 - 74))}{6 + (1 + (80 - 3))} := \frac{5 + (2 + (9 + 74))}{(6 \times (18 - 0)) - 3} := \frac{5 + (2 + (97 + 4))}{6 \times (18 - (0 - 3))} \\ &:= \frac{5 + (29 - (7 \times 4))}{6 + (1^{803})} := \frac{5 \times (2 + ((9 + 7) \times 4))}{(6 - 1) \times (80 - 3)} := \frac{((5^2) \times (9 + 7)) - 4}{6 \times (1 \times (80 - 3))} := \frac{5 + (2 + ((9 \times 7) - 4))}{(6 + 1) \times (8 - (0 - 3))} \\ &:= \frac{(52 - (9 + 7)) \times 4}{(6 + 1) \times (8 \times (03))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{59147}{86032} &:= \frac{5 + (9 + (1 \times (4 - 7)))}{8 + (6 - ((0 \times 3) - 2))} := \frac{5 + (9 + ((1^4) + 7))}{8 \times (6 + ((0 \times 3) - 2))} := \frac{(5 \times (9 - (1^4))) - 7}{8 \times (6 - (0 \times 32))} := \frac{5 \times (9 - (1 + (4 - 7)))}{(8 \times (6 - 0)) + 32} \\ &:= \frac{59 + (14 - 7)}{8 \times (6 - (0 - (3 \times 2)))} := \frac{59 + (1 + (4 \times 7))}{8 \times ((6 \times (03)) - 2)} := \frac{5 + (91 - (4 - 7))}{8 \times ((6 - (0 - 3)) \times 2)} := \frac{(5 + (9 \times 1)) \times (4 + 7)}{8 \times (60 - 32)} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times (((9 + 1) \times 4) - 7)}{8 \times (6 \times ((03 + 2)))} := \frac{5 - (9 - (1 + 47))}{8 \times (6 - ((0 \times 3) - 2))} := \frac{((5 \times (9 - 1)) + 4) \times 7}{(8 + (6^{03})) \times 2} := \frac{((5 \times 9) + 1) \times (4 + 7)}{8 \times (60 + 32)} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + 91) \times (4 + 7)}{8 \times (6 \times (032))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{68159}{73402} &:= \frac{(6 - 8) \times (1 - (5 + 9))}{(7 + (3 + (4 - 0))) \times 2} := \frac{(6 \times (8 \times (1^5))) - 9}{7 \times (3 \times (4 + (0 - 2)))} := \frac{6 - (8 - ((1 + 5) \times 9))}{7 + ((3 + (4 - 0))^2)} := \frac{6 \times (8 + (1 - (5 - 9)))}{7 \times (3 \times (4 - (0 \times 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - (8 - 15)) \times 9}{7 \times (3 \times (4 - (0 - 2)))} := \frac{6 \times (((8 - 1) \times 5) - 9)}{7 \times (3 \times (4 \times (02)))} := \frac{(6 + (8 - 1)) \times (5 + 9)}{(7 + (3 + (4 - 0)))^2} := \frac{6 \times ((8 \times (1 + 5)) - 9)}{7 \times (34 - (0 - 2))} \\ &:= \frac{6 \times (8 - (1 - (5 \times 9)))}{7 \times (3 \times (4^{02}))} := \frac{6 + (81 - (5 - 9))}{7 \times ((3 + (4 - 0)) \times 2)} := \frac{(6 + (8 - 1)) \times 59}{7 \times ((3 \times 40) - 2)} := \frac{68 + (1 + (5 - 9))}{7 \times ((3 \times (4 - 0)) - 2)} \\ &:= \frac{6 - (8 - (1 + (5 + 9)))}{7 + (3 + (4 - (0 \times 2)))} \end{aligned}$$

• **Four Digit's Numerator**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1653}{429780} &:= \frac{(((1^6) + 5)^3)}{(4 \times (2 \times (9 \times 780)))} := \frac{((1^6) + 53)}{((4 - 2) \times (9 \times 780))} := \frac{((1 + (6 - 5)) \times 3)}{(((4^2) \times 97) + (8 - 0))} := \frac{(1 - (6 - (5 + 3)))}{(4 \times ((29 \times 7) - (8 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times ((6 + 5) \times 3))}{((4 - (2 - 9)) \times 780)} := \frac{(1 \times (6 - (5 - 3)))}{((4 + (2 \times (9 \times 7))) \times (8 - 0))} := \frac{(1 \times (6 + (5 \times 3)))}{(((4^2) - 9) \times 780)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (6 + (5 - 3)))}{(4 \times ((2 + (9 \times 7)) \times (8 - 0)))} := \frac{(1^{653})}{4 + 2^{9+7-8+0}} := \frac{(1 + ((6 - 5)^3))}{(4 \times (2 \times (9 + (7 \times (8 - 0)))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (6 + (5^3)))}{(4 \times ((2 + 9) \times 780))} := \frac{(1 + (6 + (5 - 3)))}{(4 \times ((2^9) - (7 - 80)))} := \frac{(165 - 3)}{((4 + 2) \times (9 \times 780))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1894}{236750} &:= \frac{((1 + (8 + 9)) \times 4)}{(((2 \times 3) + 6) \times 750)} := \frac{((1 + 8) \times (9 \times 4))}{(2 \times (3 \times 6750))} := \frac{((18 + 9) \times 4)}{(2 \times ((3 + 6) \times 750))} := \frac{((18 - 9) \times 4)}{(2 \times ((3 + (6 \times 7)) \times 50))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - ((8 - 9) \times 4))}{(2 + 3)^{6-7+5-0}} := \frac{(1 - (8 - (9 + 4)))}{((2 \times 3) - (6 - 750))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 - (9 - 4)))}{((2 - (3 - 6)) \times (75 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (9 \times 4)))}{((2^3) \times (6 \times 750))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 + 94))}{((23 - 6) \times 750)} := \frac{(1^{894})}{(2 + (3 \times (6 + (7 \times (5 - 0)))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (8 - (9 - 4)))}{((2^{3+6}) - (7 + (5 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + (8 + (9 + 4)))}{(((2^3) \times 6) + 7) \times 50} := \frac{(1 + (8 + (9 - 4)))}{((2 - (3 - 6)) \times (7 \times 50))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{2394}{167580} &:= \frac{(((2 \times 3) + 9) \times 4)}{((1 + 6) \times (75 \times (8 - 0)))} := \frac{((2 \times (3 \times 9)) + 4)}{((1^6) \times (7 \times 580))} := \frac{((2 \times (3 + 9)) + 4)}{((1 + 6) \times (7 \times (5 \times (8 - 0))))} := \frac{((2 \times 3) - (9 - 4))}{(1 \times (67 - (5 - (8 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{((2^3) \times (9 + 4))}{((16 + 75) \times 80)} := \frac{((2^3) \times (9 - 4))}{((1^6) \times (7 \times (5 \times 80)))} := \frac{((2 + (3 \times 9)) \times 4)}{((1 + (6 + 7)) \times 580)} \\ &:= \frac{((2 + (3 + 9)) \times 4)}{(((1 + 6)^{7-5}) \times 80)} := \frac{(2 - (3 - (9 - 4)))}{((1^6) \times (7 \times (5 \times (8 - 0))))} := \frac{(2 \times ((3 + 9) \times 4))}{((1 + 6) \times ((7 + 5) \times 80))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (3 + (9 + 4)))}{((16 + (7 + 5)) \times 80)} := \frac{(2 \times (3 + (9 - 4)))}{((16 \times 75) - 80)} := \frac{(2 + (3 \times (9 - 4)))}{((1 + (6 + 7)) \times (5 + 80))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{2894}{361750} &:= \frac{(((2 \times 8) + 9) \times 4)}{(((3^6 - 1) + 7) \times 50)} := \frac{(((2 \times 8) - 9) \times 4)}{((3 + (6 + 1)) \times (7 \times 50))} := \frac{((2 - (8 - 9)) \times 4)}{((36 + (1 - 7)) \times 50)} := \frac{((2 \times (8 - 9)) + 4)}{((3 - (6 - (1 + 7))) \times 50)} \\ &:= \frac{((2 \times 8) + (9 - 4))}{((36 - 1) \times (75 - 0))} := \frac{((2^8) + (9 \times 4))}{(((3^6) + (1^7)) \times 50)} := \frac{((2 + (8 + 9)) \times 4)}{(((3 \times 61) + 7) \times 50)} \\ &:= \frac{((2 + (8 - 9)) \times 4)}{((3 + (6 + (1^7))) \times 50)} := \frac{((2 + (8 - 9))^4)}{(3 + (61 \times (7 - (5 - 0))))} := \frac{((28 \times 9) - 4)}{((3 + 617) \times 50)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (8 - (9 - 4)))}{(3 \times ((6 - (1^7)) \times 50))} := \frac{(2 + (8 - (9 - 4)))}{(3 + (617 + (5 - 0)))} := \frac{(2 + (8 \times (9 - 4)))}{((3 + (6 \times 17)) \times 50)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{2918}{364750} &:= \frac{((2 \times (9 \times 1)) + 8)}{((3 + 647) \times (5 - 0))} := \frac{((2 \times (9 - 1)) + 8)}{((3 + (64 - 7)) \times 50)} := \frac{((2 \times (9 - 1)) - 8)}{((3 + (6 + (4 + 7))) \times 50)} := \frac{((29 + 1) \times 8)}{((36 + 4) \times 750)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (9 - (1 \times 8)))}{((3 - (6 - (4 \times 7))) \times (5 - 0))} := \frac{(2 \times (9 \times (1 + 8)))}{((3 + (6 \times 4)) \times 750)} := \frac{(2 \times (9 \times (1^8)))}{(3 \times ((6 + 4) \times (75 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (9 + (1 + 8)))}{(3 \times ((6 - 4) \times 750))} := \frac{(2 \times (9 + 18))}{((3^6 - 4) \times 750)} := \frac{(2 + (9 - (1 \times 8)))}{((3 + (6 - 4)) \times (75 - 0))} := \frac{(2 + (9 - (1^8)))}{((3 - (6 - (4 \times 7))) \times 50)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (9 \times (1 \times 8)))}{(((3 \times 64) - 7) \times 50)} := \frac{(29 + (1^8))}{((3 + (6 - 4)) \times 750)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4083}{179652} &:= \frac{((4 - (0 - 8)) \times 3)}{((1 + (796 - 5)) \times 2)} := \frac{((4 \times (0 \times 8)) + 3)}{(1 \times ((7 + ((9 \times 6) + 5)) \times 2))} := \frac{((4 \times (0 + 8)) - 3)}{((1 + (7 \times (96 - 5))) \times 2)} := \frac{(4 - ((0 \times 8) - 3))}{(1 \times (7 \times (96 - 52)))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - (0 - (8 + 3)))}{(17 - (9 - 652))} := \frac{(4 - (0 - (8 - 3)))}{(1 + ((7^9 - 6) + 52))} := \frac{(4 - (0 \times 83))}{(1 + (7 \times (9 + (6 + (5 \times 2))))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times ((0 \times 8) + 3))}{(((1 - (7 - (9 \times (6 \times 5)))) \times 2)} := \frac{(4 \times (0 + (8 \times 3)))}{(1 + (7 - (9 - (65^2))))} := \frac{(4 \times (0 + (8 + 3)))}{(1 \times ((7 + 9) \times ((6 + 5)^2))} \\ &:= \frac{(4^{0 \times 8 + 3})}{(1 + (7 + (9 \times (6 \times 52))))} := \frac{(4 + ((0 \times 8) - 3))}{(1 \times (7 - (9 + (6 - 52))))} := \frac{(40 - (8 \times 3))}{(((1 - (7 - 9))^6) - (5^2))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4513}{279806} &:= \frac{(((4 \times 5) + 1) \times 3)}{(279 \times (8 - (0 - 6)))} := \frac{((4 \times (5 + 1)) - 3)}{(((2^7) + (9 + 80)) \times 6)} := \frac{(4 - (5 - (1 \times 3)))}{(2 + (((7 + 9) \times (8 - 0)) - 6))} := \frac{(4 - (5 - (1 + 3)))}{((2 \times (7 + (9 + 80))) - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - (5 + (1 - 3)))}{(2 - ((7 - (9 + (8 - 0))) \times 6))} := \frac{(4 \times (5 - (1^3)))}{(2 \times (7 + (9 + (80 \times 6))))} := \frac{(4 \times (5 \times (1^3)))}{((2 \times (7 \times (9 + 80))) - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (5 + (1 + 3)))}{(279 \times (8 - (0 \times 6)))} := \frac{(4 \times (51 + 3))}{(279 \times (8 \times (0 + 6)))} := \frac{(4 + (5 - (1 - 3)))}{(2 + ((7 \times (98 - 0)) - 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (5 \times (1^3)))}{((2 - (7 - (98 - 0))) \times 6)} := \frac{(4 + (5 + (1 + 3)))}{(2 + (7 - (9 - 806)))} := \frac{(4 + (51 - 3))}{((2 - (7 - 9)) \times 806)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4689}{375120} &:= \frac{((4 - (6 - 8)) \times 9)}{(3 \times ((7 + 5) \times 120))} := \frac{((4 \times (6 - 8)) + 9)}{((3 + (7 - (5 + 1))) \times 20)} := \frac{((4 + (6 - 8)) \times 9)}{(((3 \times 7) + 51) \times 20)} := \frac{((4 - 6) \times (8 - 9))}{(((3^7 - 5) - 1) \times 20)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - ((6 - 8) \times 9))}{((37 + 51) \times 20)} := \frac{(4 - (6 - (8 + 9)))}{((3 + 7) \times ((5 + 1) \times 20))} := \frac{(4 - (6 \times (8 - 9)))}{((3 + 7) \times ((5 - 1) \times 20))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 - (8 - 9)))}{(((3^7) + (51 + (2 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times (6 + (8 - 9)))}{(((3 + 7) \times (5 - 1))^2 + 0)} := \frac{(4 + (6 + (8 + 9)))}{(3 \times (((7 \times 5) + 1) \times 20))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (6 + (8 - 9)))}{((3 + (7 \times 51)) \times (2 - 0))} := \frac{(4 + (68 - 9))}{((37 + 5) \times 120)} := \frac{(46 + (8 - 9))}{(((3 + 7) \times (5 + 1))^2 + 0)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4968}{217350} &:= \frac{(((4 \times 9) + 6) \times 8)}{(2 \times (1 \times 7350))} := \frac{(((4 \times 9) - 6) \times 8)}{(21 \times ((7 + 3) \times 50))} := \frac{((4 - (9 - 6)) \times 8)}{(2 + (1 \times ((7^3) + (5 - 0))))} := \frac{((4 \times (9 \times 6)) + 8)}{((21 + 7) \times 350)} \\ &:= \frac{((4 \times (9 - 6)) + 8)}{((2 + 173) \times (5 - 0))} := \frac{((4 \times (9 - 6)) - 8)}{((2^{1 \times 7}) - (3 - 50))} := \frac{((4 \times 96) + 8)}{((2 - 1) \times ((7^3) \times 50))} \\ &:= \frac{((4^{9-6}) + 8)}{((2 + (1 \times 7)) \times 350)} := \frac{((4^{9-6}) - 8)}{((2 - 1) \times (7 \times 350))} := \frac{((4 + (9 + 6)) \times 8)}{((2 + 17) \times 350)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times ((9 - 6) \times 8))}{(21 \times ((7 - 3) \times 50))} := \frac{(4 \times (9 \times (6 + 8)))}{(21 \times (7 \times (3 \times 50)))} := \frac{(4 \times (96 + 8))}{((21 + (7^3)) \times 50)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{5091}{468372} &:= \frac{((5 \times (0 \times 9)) + 1)}{(4 + (6 + (8 + (37 \times 2))))} := \frac{((5 \times (0 + 9)) + 1)}{(46 \times (83 + (7 + 2)))} := \frac{((5 \times (0 + 9)) - 1)}{(46 \times (83 + (7 - 2)))} := \frac{(5 - ((0 \times 9) - 1))}{(4 \times (6 \times (8 + (3 \times (7 - 2)))))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 - (0 - (9 \times 1)))}{(4 \times ((6 + 8) \times ((3 \times 7) + 2)))} := \frac{(5 - (0 - (9 - 1)))}{((4 + (6 \times 8)) \times ((3 \times 7) + 2))} := \frac{(5 - (0 \times 91))}{(4 \times ((6 \times (8 + 3)) + (7^2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 \times (0 + (9 \times 1)))}{(46 \times ((8 + 37) \times 2))} := \frac{(5 \times (0 + (9 - 1)))}{((4^6) - (8 \times (3 + (7^2))))} := \frac{(5 + ((0 \times 9) - 1))}{(4 \times ((6 - 8) \times (3 - (7^2))))} \\ &:= \frac{(50 - (9 \times 1))}{(46 \times (8 + (37 \times 2)))} := \frac{(50 \times (9 - 1))}{(46 \times (8 \times ((3 + 7)^2))} := \frac{(50 + (9 + 1))}{(4 \times ((683 + 7) \times 2))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{5319}{468072} &:= \frac{((5 \times (3 \times 1)) - 9)}{(4 \times (6 \times (8 - (0 - (7 \times 2)))))} := \frac{((5 \times 3) - (1 + 9))}{(4 + ((6 \times (80 - 7)) - 2))} := \frac{(5 - (3 - (1^9)))}{((4 \times (6 \times (8 - 0))) + 72)} := \frac{(5 - (3 \times (1^9)))}{((4^6) - (80 \times (7^2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 - (3 + (1^9)))}{(4 \times (6 - (8 \times ((0 \times 7) - 2))))} := \frac{(5 - (3 - 19))}{((4 \times (6 \times 80)) - 72)} := \frac{(5 \times (3 - (1^9)))}{(4 + (6 \times ((80 - 7) \times 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 \times (3 + (1^9)))}{(4 \times ((6 \times (80 - 7)) + 2))} := \frac{(5 + ((3 + 1) \times 9))}{((46 \times 80) - 72)} := \frac{(5 + (3 - (1^9)))}{(4 - (68 \times (0 - (7 + 2))))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + (3 + (1 + 9)))}{(4 \times (6 \times (80 - (7 \times 2))))} := \frac{(53 - (1 + 9))}{(4 \times (((6 \times 80) - 7) \times 2))} := \frac{(53 + (1^9))}{(4680 + 72)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{5796}{104328} &:= \frac{((5 \times 7) - (9 - 6))}{((10 + ((4^3) - 2)) \times 8)} := \frac{((5 + (7 - 9)) \times 6)}{(1 \times (0 - (4 - 328)))} := \frac{((5 + 7) \times (9 - 6))}{(((10 - (4 - 3))^2) \times 8)} := \frac{(5 - ((7 - 9) \times 6))}{((104 \times 3) + (2 - 8))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 - (7 - (9 \times 6)))}{(104 \times (3 - (2 - 8)))} := \frac{(5 - (7 - (9 + 6)))}{(10 - ((4 - 32) \times 8))} := \frac{(5 - (7 - (9 - 6)))}{(1 - (0 - (4 + (3 + (2 + 8)))))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 \times (7 - (9 - 6)))}{(1 \times (0 + ((43 + 2) \times 8)))} := \frac{(5 + (7 - (9 - 6)))}{(10 + (((4 \times 3)^2) + 8))} := \frac{(5 + (7 + (9 - 6)))}{(10 + (4 + (32 \times 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + (7 + 96))}{(((1 - (0 - 43))^2) + 8)} := \frac{(57 - (9 \times 6))}{(1 - (0 - (43 + (2 + 8))))} := \frac{(57 + 96)}{(((10 + 4)^3) + (2 + 8))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{5814}{372096} &:= \frac{((5 \times (8 - 1)) - 4)}{((3^7) - (209 - 6))} := \frac{((5^8 \times 1) \times 4)}{(3 + 7)^{2^{9-6}}} := \frac{(5 - (8 - (1 + 4)))}{(3 + ((7 \times 20) - (9 + 6)))} := \frac{(5 \times (8 + (1^4)))}{((3 + (7 + 20)) \times 96)} \\ &:= \frac{(5^{8-1-4})}{(((3 + 7) \times (2 - 0))^{9-6})} := \frac{(5 + (8 - (1 \times 4)))}{((3 - (7 + 2)) \times (0 - 96))} := \frac{(5 + (8 - (1^4)))}{((3 + (7 - (2 - 0))) \times 96)} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + (8 - (1 + 4)))}{((3 + (7 - (2 - 0)))^{9-6})} := \frac{(5 + (8 \times (1 \times 4)))}{(37 \times (2^{0 \times 9 + 6}))} := \frac{(5 + (8 + (1 + 4)))}{((3 + (7 + (2 - 0))) \times 96)} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + (8 + (1 - 4)))}{((3 + 7) \times (2^{0 \times 9 + 6}))} := \frac{(5 + (8 + 14))}{((3 + (7 + (2 - 0)))^{9-6})} := \frac{(58 + (1 + 4))}{(3 \times (7 \times (2 \times (0 + 96))))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{6435}{218790} &:= \frac{(((6 \times 4) + 3) \times 5)}{(2 - ((1 - 8) \times 7)) \times 90} := \frac{(((6 \times (4 + 3)) + 5)}{(2 \times (1 + (8 + 790)))} := \frac{((6 \times 4) - (3 \times 5))}{(2 \times (((1 + 8) \times 7) + 90))} := \frac{(6 - ((4 - 3) \times 5))}{(2 \times (1 - (8 \times (7 - (9 - 0)))))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - ((4 - 3)^5))}{((21 \times 8) - (7 - (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(6 - (4 + (3 - 5)))}{(2 - (1 - ((8 + 7) \times (9 - 0))))} := \frac{6^{(4-3)^5}}{((2 \times (1 + (8 \times 7))) + 90)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + (4 - (3 + 5)))}{(2 + (1 + ((8 \times 7) + (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(6 + (4 + (3 - 5)))}{(2 \times (1 + ((8 + 7) \times (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(6 + (4 + 35))}{((2 + (1 \times (8 + 7))) \times 90)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + (43 + 5))}{((21 \times 87) + (9 - 0))} := \frac{(6 + (43 - 5))}{(2 - (18 \times (7 - 90)))} := \frac{(64 + 35)}{(2 \times (187 \times (9 - 0)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7596}{341820} &:= \frac{(((7-5) \times 9) - 6)}{((3^4 - 1^8) \times 20)} := \frac{((7 \times 5) - (9 + 6))}{((3^4) - (1 - 820))} := \frac{((7 \times 5) - (9 - 6))}{(3 \times ((4 - 1) \times (8 \times 20)))} := \frac{((7 + (5 - 9)) \times 6)}{((3^4 \times 1) \times (8 + (2 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 + 5) \times (9 \times 6))}{((3^4) \times (18 \times 20))} := \frac{((7 + 5) \times (9 + 6))}{(((3^4) + (1 + 8))^2 + 0)} := \frac{((7 + 5) \times (9 - 6))}{3^4 \times 1^8 \times 20} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 - 5) \times (9 - 6))}{(((3^4 - 1) \times (8 + (2 - 0))))} := \frac{(7 - (5 - (9 - 6)))}{((3 \times (4 + (1^8)))^2 + 0)} := \frac{(7 \times (5 + (9 - 6)))}{((3 + 4) \times (18 \times 20))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (5 - (9 - 6)))}{(341 + (8^2 + 0))} := \frac{(7 + (5 \times (9 - 6)))}{(3 \times ((41 \times 8) + (2 - 0)))} := \frac{(7 + (5 + 96))}{((3^4 + 1^8) \times 20)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7803}{429165} &:= \frac{((7 \times (8 - 0)) + 3)}{((4 + 291) \times (6 + 5))} := \frac{((7 \times (8 - 0)) - 3)}{(4 + (2916 - 5))} := \frac{((7 + (8 - 0)) \times 3)}{((4 + (2 + 9)) \times 165)} := \frac{((7 - 8) \times (0 - 3))}{((4 + (2 + (9 \times 1))) \times (6 + 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 - (8 \times (0 \times 3)))}{((4 - (2 - 9)) \times ((1 + 6) \times 5))} := \frac{(7 - (8 + (0 - 3)))}{(4 - (2 - (9 \times (1 + (6 + 5))))))} := \frac{(7 \times (8 + (0 - 3)))}{(((42 \times 9) + (1 + 6)) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (8 - (0 - 3)))}{((4 + (2 \times (91 + 6))) \times 5)} := \frac{(7 + (8 + (0 - 3)))}{(4 \times ((2 \times (91 - 6)) - 5))} := \frac{(7 + (80 - 3))}{(42 \times ((9 + 1) \times (6 + 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(78 - (0 \times 3))}{(4291 - (6 - 5))} := \frac{(78 \times (0 + 3))}{(429 \times (1 \times (6 \times 5)))} := \frac{(78 + (0 - 3))}{(((4^2) + 9) \times 165)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7812}{453096} &:= \frac{((7 \times (8 \times 1)) + 2)}{(4 + ((5 + 30) \times 96))} := \frac{((7 + (8 \times 1)) \times 2)}{(((4 \times 5) + (30 \times 9)) \times 6)} := \frac{(7 - (8 - (1 \times 2)))}{(4 + ((5 \times (3 - (0 - 9))) - 6))} := \frac{(7 - (8 - (1 + 2)))}{(4 \times (5 - (30 - (9 \times 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 \times (8 - (1 \times 2)))}{(((4 + 5) \times (30 \times 9)) + 6)} := \frac{(7 \times (8 + (1^2)))}{(((4 \times (5 \times 30)) + 9) \times 6)} := \frac{(7 + ((8 - 1) \times 2))}{(((4 \times (53 - 0)) - 9) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (8 - (1 \times 2)))}{4 + 5^{3+0 \times 9} \times 6} := \frac{(7 + (8 - (1 + 2)))}{((4 \times (5 \times 30)) + 96)} := \frac{(7 + (8 \times (1^2)))}{((4 + ((5 \times 30) - 9)) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (8 + 12))}{((4 - (5 - 30)) \times (9 \times 6))} := \frac{(7 + (8 - 12))}{(((4 + 5) \times 30) - 96)} := \frac{(78 \times (1^2))}{(4 \times (((5^3 + 0) \times 9) + 6))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7946}{135082} &:= \frac{((7 - (9 - 4)) \times 6)}{((1 - 35) \times (0 - (8 - 2)))} := \frac{((7 - (9 - 4))^6)}{(((1 + 3)^5 + 0) + (8^2))} := \frac{((7 \times (9 \times 4)) - 6)}{(((1^3) + 50) \times 82)} := \frac{((7 \times 9) - (4 + 6))}{(1 + (3 \times (50 \times (8 - 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 \times 9) - 46)}{(((1 + (3 + (5 - (0 - 8))))^2)} := \frac{((7 + (9 + 4)) \times 6)}{(1 + 3) \times (508 + 2)} := \frac{((7 - 9) \times (4 - 6))}{(1 \times ((3 \times 50) - 82))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 - (9 - (4 + 6)))}{(1 + (3 + (50 + 82)))} := \frac{(7 + (9 - (4 + 6)))}{(1 \times (3 \times (50 - (8 \times 2))))} := \frac{(7 + (9 - (4 - 6)))}{(((1^3) + 50) \times (8 - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (9 + (4 + 6)))}{(13 \times (50 - (8 \times 2)))} := \frac{(7 + (9 + (4 - 6)))}{(1 + ((3^5 + 0) - (8 - 2)))} := \frac{(79 - 46)}{(1 - (35 \times (0 - (8 \times 2))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{8269}{140573} &:= \frac{(((8 - 2) \times 6) + 9)}{(140 + (5^{7-3}))} := \frac{((8 \times 2) - (6 + 9))}{(1 - (4 + (0 - (5 \times (7 - 3))))))} := \frac{((8 \times 2) - (6 - 9))}{(1 \times ((4 \times (0 - 5)) + (7^3)))} := \frac{(8 - ((2 \times 6) - 9))}{(1 - (4 \times ((0 \times 5) - (7 \times 3))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 - ((2 - 6) \times 9))}{(1 \times (405 + (7^3)))} := \frac{(8 - (2 - (6 \times 9)))}{(1 \times ((4^{05}) - (7 - 3)))} := \frac{(8 - (2 - (6 + 9)))}{(14 - ((0 \times 5) - (7^3)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 - (2 - (6 - 9)))}{(1 - (4 + (0 - (57 - 3))))} := \frac{(8 - (2 + (6 - 9)))}{(1 - (4 \times (0 - ((5 \times 7) + 3))))} := \frac{(8 + ((2 \times 6) + 9))}{((14 \times (0 + (5 \times 7))) + 3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 + (2 - (6 - 9)))}{(1 \times ((40 \times 5) + (7 \times 3)))} := \frac{(8 + (2 \times (6 - 9)))}{(1 + ((4 - ((0 \times 5) - 7)) \times 3))} := \frac{(8 + (2 + (6 - 9)))}{(1 + (40 + (5 + 73)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{8934}{125076} &:= \frac{(((8 \times 9) + 3) \times 4)}{(1 \times (2 \times (50 \times (7 \times 6))))} := \frac{((8 - (9 - 3)) \times 4)}{(125 + (0 - (7 + 6)))} := \frac{((8 \times 9) + (3^4))}{(((1^2) + 50) \times (7 \times 6))} := \frac{((8 \times 9) - 34)}{(1 \times ((2 + (5 - 0)) \times 76))} \\
 &:= \frac{((8 - 9) \times (3 - 4))}{(1 \times (2 - ((5 + (0 - 7)) \times 6)))} := \frac{(8 - (9 - (3 + 4)))}{(1 + (2 + (5 - (0 - 76))))} := \frac{(8 - (9 \times (3 - 4)))}{(1 + (250 - (7 + 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 - (9 - 34))}{((1 + (2 \times (5 - 0))) \times (7 \times 6))} := \frac{(8 + (9 - (3 \times 4)))}{(1 - (2 + (5 + (0 - 76))))} := \frac{(8 + (9 - (3 - 4)))}{(1 \times (2 \times (50 + 76)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 + (9 + (3 + 4)))}{((1 - (2 - (50 + 7))) \times 6)} := \frac{(8 + (9 + 34))}{((12 + (5 - 0)) \times (7 \times 6))} := \frac{(89 + (3 + 4))}{(1 \times ((2^5 + 0) \times (7 \times 6)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9342}{105876} &:= \frac{9 - (3 \times (4 - 2))}{((1 + (0 - (5 - 8))) \times 7) + 6} := \frac{9 + (3 - (4 + 2))}{1 - (0 - (5 + ((8 \times 7) + 6)))} := \frac{9 - (3 - (4 + 2))}{(1 + (0 - 5)) \times (8 - (7 \times 6))} := \frac{9 + (3 \times (4 - 2))}{1 \times (0 - (5 \times (8 - (7 \times 6))))} \\ &:= \frac{9 + (3^4 - 2)}{(1 - (0 - ((5 \times 8) - 7))) \times 6} := \frac{(9 \times 3) - (4 + 2)}{10 - ((5 - 8) \times 76)} := \frac{(9 + 3) \times (4 - 2)}{(1 + (0 - 5)) \times (8 - 76)} := \frac{(9 + (3 \times 4)) \times 2}{(10 \times ((5 \times 8) + 7)) + 6} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times (3 + (4 - 2))}{(10 + (5 \times (8 + 7))) \times 6} := \frac{9 + (3 + 42)}{(10 + (5 + 87)) \times 6} := \frac{9 + (3 \times (4 + 2))}{1 \times (0 - ((5 - (8 \times 7)) \times 6))} := \frac{(9 - 3) \times 42}{(10 + 58) \times (7 \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{9 \times ((3 + 4)^2)}{((105 \times 8) - 7) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9534}{162078} &:= \frac{(((9 - 5) \times 3) - 4)}{(1 + ((6 \times 20) + (7 + 8)))} := \frac{(9 - ((5 - 3) \times 4))}{(1 - (6 + ((2 \times (0 - 7)) - 8)))} := \frac{(9 - (5 - (3 \times 4)))}{((1 + (6 + (20 + 7))) \times 8)} := \frac{(9 - (5 - (3 - 4)))}{(1 \times ((6^2 + 0) + (7 + 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 - (5 + (3 - 4)))}{(((1 - (6 \times 2)) \times (0 - 7)) + 8)} := \frac{(9 + ((5 - 3) \times 4))}{(1 + ((6^{2+0 \times 7}) \times 8))} := \frac{(9 + (5 - (3 \times 4)))}{(((1 + 6)^2 + 0) - (7 + 8))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 + (5 - (3 + 4)))}{(1 + (6 - (2 \times (0 - (7 \times 8))))))} := \frac{(9 + (5 - (3 - 4)))}{((16^2 + 0) + (7 - 8))} := \frac{(9 + (5 \times (3 - 4)))}{(1 \times ((6 \times (2 - 0)) + (7 \times 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 + (5 + (3 \times 4)))}{(1 \times ((62 \times (0 + 7)) + 8))} := \frac{(9 + (5 + (3 - 4)))}{(1 \times (6 + (207 + 8)))} := \frac{(9 + (5 + 34))}{(1 \times (6 \times ((2^{07}) + 8)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9638}{120475} &:= \frac{(((9 \times 6) + 3) \times 8)}{(12 \times (0 + 475))} := \frac{((9 - (6 - 3)) \times 8)}{(1 \times (2 \times (0 + (4 \times 75))))} := \frac{((9 \times 6) - (3 \times 8))}{(((1^2 + 0) + 4) \times 75)} := \frac{((9 \times 6) - 38)}{((12 - (0 - (4 \times 7))) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{((9 + (6 + 3)) \times 8)}{(1 \times ((20 + 4) \times 75))} := \frac{((9 + (6 - 3)) \times 8)}{(1 \times ((2^{04}) \times 75))} := \frac{((9 - 6) \times 38)}{((1 + (2 - 0)) \times 475)} \\ &:= \frac{((96 - 3) \times 8)}{((120 + 4) \times 75)} := \frac{(9 - (6 - (3 + 8)))}{(((1^2 + 0) + 4) \times (7 \times 5))} := \frac{(9 - (6 + (3 - 8)))}{(1 - ((2 \times (0 - 47)) - 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 + (6 - (3 + 8)))}{(1 \times (2 - (0 - (4 \times (7 + 5))))))} := \frac{(9 + (6 - (3 - 8)))}{((1 + (2 - (0 - 47))) \times 5)} := \frac{(96 - (3 \times 8))}{((1 + (2 - 0)) \times (4 \times 75))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9756}{102438} &:= \frac{9 + (7 \times (5 - 6))}{1 \times (((02^4) - (3 - 8)))} := \frac{((9 - 7) \times 5) - 6}{1 \times (0 - (2 - (4 \times (3 + 8))))} := \frac{9 - (7 \times (5 - 6))}{1 \times (((024 - 3) \times 8))} := \frac{(9 \times (7 - 5)) + 6}{1 - (0 - (243 + 8))} \\ &:= \frac{9 - (7 - (5 \times 6))}{(1 + (0 - (2 - 43))) \times 8} := \frac{(9 - (7 - 5)) \times 6}{1 - (0 - (2 + 438))} := \frac{9 - (7 - 56)}{1 - (0 - ((2^4) \times 38))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 \times 7) - (5 - 6)}{(((1 - (0 - 2))^4) + 3) \times 8} := \frac{(9 \times (7 - 5)) - 6}{(1 - (0 - 2)) \times (4 + 38)} := \frac{97 + 5 - 6}{10^{2+4-3} + 8} := \frac{97 - 5 + 6}{1024 - 3 + 8} \\ &:= \frac{((9 \times 7) + 5) \times 6}{102 \times (4 + 38)} := \frac{(9 + 7) \times (5 \times 6)}{10 \times (((2 \times 4)^3) - 8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9781}{254306} &:= \frac{(((9 - 7) \times 8) + 1)}{(2 \times ((5 \times (43 - 0)) + 6))} := \frac{(((9 - 7) \times 8) - 1)}{(((2^5) \times (4 \times (3 - 0))) + 6)} := \frac{((9 \times 7) - (8 \times 1))}{((2 \times (5^4)) + (30 \times 6))} := \frac{(9 - 7) \times (8 + 1)}{(2 \times ((5 + (4 + 30)) \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 - (7 - (8 - 1)))}{((25 - (4^3)) \times (0 - 6))} := \frac{(9 - (7 - 81))}{(2 + ((5 \times 430) + 6))} := \frac{(9 \times (7 + (8 + 1)))}{((2 + ((5^4) - (3 - 0))) \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(9 + (7 - (8 \times 1)))}{(((2^5) - (4 - (30 \times 6)))} := \frac{(9 + (7 - (8 + 1)))}{(2 + (5 \times (4 \times (3 - (0 - 6))))))} := \frac{(9 + (7 + (8 \times 1)))}{(2 + ((5^4) + (3 + (0 - 6))))} \\ &:= \frac{(97 + (8 \times 1))}{((25 + 430) \times 6)} := \frac{(97 + (8 + 1))}{(2 + ((5 + 4) \times 306))} := \frac{(97 - 81)}{(2 + ((5 + (4^3 + 0)) \times 6))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9846}{172305} &:= \frac{(((9 + 8) \times 4) - 6)}{((1 + (72 \times (3 - 0))) \times 5)} := \frac{(((9 - 8)^4) \times 6)}{(((1^7) + 2) \times (30 + 5))} := \frac{((9 - (8 - 4)) \times 6)}{((1 + (7 \times 2)) \times (30 + 5))} := \frac{((9 \times (8 - 4)) + 6)}{(1 \times ((7^2) \times (3 \times (0 + 5))))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 \times 8) - (4 \times 6)}{((1 - 7) \times ((2 - 30) \times 5))} := \frac{(9 \times 8) + (4 - 6)}{(1 \times ((7^2) \times (30 - 5)))} := \frac{(9 \times 8) - 46}{(1 \times (7 \times ((2 \times 30) + 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 - 8) \times (4 + 6)}{(1 \times ((7 - (2 - 30)) \times 5))} := \frac{(9 - 8) \times 46}{(1 \times (7 \times (23 \times (0 + 5))))} := \frac{(9 \times (8 - (4 - 6)))}{(1 \times (7 \times (230 - 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{(98 - (4 \times 6))}{(((17^2) - 30) \times 5)} := \frac{(98 - (4 - 6))}{((1 + (7^2)) \times (30 + 5))} := \frac{(98 + 46)}{(1 \times (72 \times (30 + 5)))} \end{aligned}$$

3.13 14 Equivalent Blocks

• Five Digit's Numertor

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14835}{20769} &:= \frac{(((1-(4-8))^3)+5)}{(2^{07})+(6 \times 9)} := \frac{(((1^4)+8) \times (3 \times 5))}{((20+(7-6)) \times 9)} := \frac{((1+4) \times (8+(3 \times 5)))}{((2 \times (0+76))+9)} := \frac{(1-(4-(8+35)))}{(2-((0 \times 7)-(6 \times 9)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1-(4-(83+5)))}{(2-(0-((7+6) \times 9)))} := \frac{(1-(4-(83-5)))}{(20+(76+9))} := \frac{(1 \times ((4+(8-3)) \times 5))}{(1+(4-(8 \times (3-5))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1+((4 \times 8)-(3-5)))}{(2+(0-(7-(6 \times 9))))} := \frac{(1+((48 \times 3)+5))}{(2-(0-(7+(6 \times 9))))} := \frac{(1+(4-(8-(3+5))))}{(1 \times (4-(8 \times (3-5))))} \\ &:= \frac{(2+(0-(7-(6 \times 9))))}{(1+(4+((8-3) \times 5)))} := \frac{(2 \times (0+(7 \times (6+9))))}{(1+((48 \times 3)+5))} := \frac{(2-(0-(7-(6 \times 9))))}{((2 \times (0-(7-6)))+9)} := \frac{(20-(7-(6+9)))}{((2 \times (0+(7+6)))+9)} \\ &:= \frac{(1+(4+((8-3) \times 5)))}{(2 \times (0-(7 \times (6-9))))} := \frac{(1+(4+(8-(3-5))))}{((2 \times ((0 \times 7)+6))+9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{16758}{23940} &:= \frac{(((1+6)^{7-5}) \times 8)}{((2+(3+9)) \times 40)} := \frac{(((1^6)-(7-(5+8))))}{(2+(3+(9-(4-0))))} := \frac{((1+(6+7)) \times (5^8))}{(((2+3)^9) \times (4-0))} := \frac{((1+(6+7)) \times 58)}{((2+(3 \times 9)) \times 40)} \\ &:= \frac{((1+6) \times ((7+5) \times 8))}{(2 \times ((3+9) \times 40))} := \frac{(((16+(7+5)) \times 8))}{((2-(3-9)) \times 40)} := \frac{(1-((6-(7+5)) \times 8))}{(2 \times (39-(4-0)))} := \frac{(1-((6-7) \times (5+8)))}{((2 \times (3+9))-(4-0))} \\ &:= \frac{(1-(6-(7+(5 \times 8))))}{(((2 \times 3)+9) \times (4-0))} := \frac{(1 \times (67-(5-8)))}{((2 \times 3)+(94-0))} := \frac{(1+((6 \times (7-5))+8))}{(2-(3+(9-40)))} := \frac{(1+((6+(7 \times 5)) \times 8))}{((2+3) \times (94-0))} \\ &:= \frac{(1+(6-(7 \times (5-8))))}{((2^3) \times (9-(4-0)))} := \frac{(1+(67+58))}{((2+3) \times (9 \times (4-0)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{18359}{26704} &:= \frac{1-(8+((3-5) \times 9))}{2^{(-6+7) \times 04}} := \frac{1+(8+((3 \times 5)+9))}{2+((6 \times (7-0))+4)} := \frac{18+(35-9)}{2^{6+7 \times 0 \times 4}} := \frac{1-(8-359)}{2^{6+7-04}} \\ &:= \frac{(1+(8-(3-5))) \times 9}{2 \times (6+(70-4))} := \frac{1 \times ((8+3) \times (5+9))}{(2+6) \times (7 \times (04))} := \frac{(((1+8) \times 3)-5) \times 9}{2+(6+(70 \times 4))} := \frac{(18+(3 \times 5)) \times 9}{2 \times (6^{7-04})} \\ &:= \frac{1-(8-(35 \times 9))}{(2^6) \times (7-(0 \times 4))} := \frac{1+((83 \times 5)-9)}{(2+6) \times (70+4)} := \frac{(1-8) \times (3-(5+9))}{(2-6) \times (7 \times (0-4))} := \frac{1+((8^3)+59)}{2 \times ((6 \times 70)-4)} \\ &:= \frac{(183 \times 5)+9}{(2 \times 670)+4} := \frac{1-(8-(3+59))}{(2 \times (6 \times (7-0)))-4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{18459}{26370} &:= \frac{1-(8-(4+(5 \times 9)))}{(2^6)+(3-(7-0))} := \frac{1-(8-(4+59))}{(2+6) \times (3+(7-0))} := \frac{1 \times (8-(4-59))}{2+((6 \times 3)+70)} := \frac{(1^{84}) \times (5+9)}{2 \times (6-(3-(7-0)))} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (84+(5 \times 9))}{2 \times (63+(7-0))} := \frac{(1+(8+4)) \times (5+9)}{26 \times (3+(7-0))} := \frac{1+(8+(4 \times (5 \times 9)))}{263+(7-0)} := \frac{1+(8+(4 \times 59))}{(2+(6-3)) \times 70} \\ &:= \frac{(18+4) \times (5+9)}{2+(6 \times (3+70))} := \frac{1 \times (8 \times (4+(5 \times 9)))}{(2^{6-3}) \times 70} := \frac{1-(8 \times (4-59))}{((2 \times 6)-3) \times 70} := \frac{1 \times (8 \times (4 \times (5+9)))}{(2^6) \times (3+(7-0))} \\ &:= \frac{18 \times (4+(5 \times 9))}{2 \times ((6+3) \times 70)} := \frac{1 \times (84 \times (5+9))}{(2+6) \times (3 \times 70)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{23490}{75168} &:= \frac{2+(3-(4-(9-0)))}{(7 \times 5)-(1-(6-8))} := \frac{(2 \times (3 \times 4))-(9-0)}{(7+(5-(1 \times 6))) \times 8} := \frac{(2 \times (3+4))-(9-0)}{7-(5-(1 \times (6+8)))} := \frac{2-(3-(4 \times (9-0)))}{7 \times (((5-1) \times 6)-8)} \\ &:= \frac{2+(34+(9-0))}{(7-(5-16)) \times 8} := \frac{2 \times (34-(9-0))}{(7 \times ((5-1) \times 6))-8} := \frac{(2 \times 3)+(49-0)}{(7 \times ((5-1) \times 6))+8} := \frac{2+((3+4) \times (9-0))}{(((7 \times 5)+1) \times 6)-8} \\ &:= \frac{2-(3 \times 4)-90}{(7-(5 \times (1^6)))^8} := \frac{2-(3+(4-90))}{((7 \times (5-1))+6) \times 8} := \frac{(2+(3-4)) \times 90}{((7 \times (5+1))-6) \times 8} := \frac{(2 \times 3)+(4+90)}{(2 \times 3)+(4+90)} \\ &:= \frac{2+(3 \times (4 \times (9-0)))}{7+(5 \times (1+68))} := \frac{2 \times ((3^4)+(9-0))}{(7+(5 \times 1)) \times (6 \times 8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{25830}{69741} &:= \frac{(((2 \times 5) + 8) \times 30)}{(6 \times (9 \times ((7 \times 4) - 1)))} := \frac{(((2 \times 5) - 8) \times 30)}{(6 \times (9 \times (7 - (4 \times 1))))} := \frac{((2 - (5 - 8)) \times 30)}{((6 + 9) \times ((7 \times 4) - 1))} := \frac{((2^5) \times (8 \times 30))}{((6 \times (9 - 7))^{4 \times 1})} \\ &:= \frac{((2^5) + (8 + 30))}{((((6 \times 9) - 7) \times 4) + 1)} := \frac{((2^5) + (8 - 30))}{(6 + (9 + (7 + (4 + 1))))} := \frac{((2 + 58) \times (3 - 0))}{6 \times 9^{7-4-1}} := \frac{(2 - (5 - (83 - 0)))}{(6 \times (9 \times (7 - (4 - 1))))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times ((5 \times 8) + 30))}{(6 \times (((9 + 7) \times 4) - 1))} := \frac{(2 \times (5 \times (8 \times (3 - 0))))}{(6 \times (9 \times (7 + (4 + 1))))} := \frac{(2 \times (5 \times (8 + (3 - 0))))}{(6 + (97 \times (4 - 1)))} := \frac{(2 \times (5 + (8 - (3 - 0))))}{(6 \times (((9 - 7) \times 4) + 1))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (5 + (83 - 0)))}{((((6 \times 9) + 7) \times 4) - 1)} := \frac{(2 + (58 - 30))}{(69 + (7 + (4 + 1)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{27135}{96480} &:= \frac{2 \times (7 - (1 \times (3 - 5)))}{96 - (4 \times (8 - 0))} := \frac{2 + (7 + (13 + 5))}{(9 - 6) \times (4 \times (8 - 0))} := \frac{27 + (1 + (3 + 5))}{96 + (4 \times (8 - 0))} := \frac{27 + (1 + 35)}{(9 \times (6 \times 4)) + (8 - 0)} \\ &:= \frac{2 + (71 + (3 + 5))}{9 \times ((6 \times 4) + (8 - 0))} := \frac{(2 + (7 \times 1)) \times (3 \times 5)}{(9 + 6) \times (4 \times (8 - 0))} := \frac{27 + 135}{96 + 480} := \frac{((2 \times 7) + 1) \times (3 \times 5)}{(96 + 4) \times (8 - 0)} \\ &:= \frac{27 + (1 \times (3^5))}{(9 - 6) \times (4 \times 80)} := \frac{(2 + 7) \times (1 + 35)}{96 \times (4 + (8 - 0))} := \frac{27 \times (1 \times (3 \times 5))}{9 \times ((6 - 4) \times 80)} \\ &:= \frac{((2 \times (7 - 1))^3) \times 5}{96 \times (4 \times 80)} := \frac{2 \times ((7 - (1 + 3))^5)}{9 \times (6 \times (4 \times (8 - 0)))} := \frac{(2 + 7) \times (1 - (3 - 5))}{9 \times (6 \times (48 - 0))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{28695}{40173} &:= \frac{(2 \times (8 + (6 - 9))) + 5}{(4 \times (0 - (1 - 7))) - 3} := \frac{2 \times (8 + (6 - (9 - 5)))}{4 - (0 - ((1 + 7) \times 3))} := \frac{2 + (8 - ((6 - 9) \times 5))}{(4 \times ((01 + 7))) + 3} := \frac{2 + (8 + (6 + (9 + 5)))}{40 - ((1^7) - 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (8 + (6 - 9))) - 5}{4 + (0 - (1 - (7 - 3)))} := \frac{(2 + (8 + (6 - 9))) \times 5}{40 - (1 - (7 + 3))} := \frac{(2 \times 8) + (6 \times (9 - 5))}{4 \times ((017 - 3))} := \frac{(2 \times 8) - (6 - (9 \times 5))}{4 - (0 - (1 \times 73))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (8 - (6 - 9))) \times 5}{40 + (17 \times 3)} := \frac{(2 \times 8) + ((6 \times 9) + 5)}{(4 - (0 - 1)) \times (7 \times 3)} := \frac{(2 \times (8 \times (6 + 9))) + 5}{(4 \times (0 \times 1)) + (7^3)} := \frac{2 - (8 - (6 + (9 \times 5)))}{(4 - (0 - 17)) \times 3} \\ &:= \frac{2 + ((8 - 6) \times (9 - 5))}{4 - (0 - (1 \times (7 + 3)))} := \frac{(2 \times 8) + (69 - 5)}{40 - (1 - 73)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{30528}{41976} &:= \frac{3 + (0 - (5 - (2 + 8)))}{4 - (1 - (9 - (7 - 6)))} := \frac{3 - (0 - (5 + (2 \times 8)))}{41 - (9 - (7 - 6))} := \frac{30 + ((5 \times 2) - 8)}{4 \times (1 + (9 + (7 - 6)))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (5 - 2))) \times 8}{(4 + ((1^9) \times 7)) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{((3 - (0 - 5))^2) - 8}{(4 \times 19) + (7 - 6)} := \frac{3 \times (((05 - 2) \times 8))}{4 - (1 - ((9 + 7) \times 6))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (5 + 2))) \times 8}{(4 \times (19 + 7)) + 6} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (5 \times 2))) \times 8}{4 + ((19 \times 7) + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(30 + 52) \times 8}{41 \times (9 + (7 + 6))} := \frac{(30 \times 5) + (2 - 8)}{((4 \times (1 + 9)) - 7) \times 6} := \frac{(3 - ((0 \times 5) - 2)) \times 8}{4 + (1 \times (9 + (7 \times 6)))} := \frac{(3^{7-4-1}) \times 8}{((4 - 1) \times 97) + 6} \\ &:= \frac{(3 - (0 - (5^2))) \times 8}{4 \times ((1^9) + 76)} := \frac{(3 \times (0 \times 5)) + (2 \times 8)}{4 + ((1 + (9 - 7)) \times 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{31590}{78624} &:= \frac{31 + (59 - 0)}{7 \times (8 \times (6 + (2 - 4)))} := \frac{3 \times (1 + (5 + (9 - 0)))}{7 \times (8 + (6 - (2 - 4)))} := \frac{(3 + (1^5)) \times 90}{7 \times (8 \times ((6 - 2) \times 4))} := \frac{3 \times (1 \times (5 \times (9 - 0)))}{7 \times (8 + ((6^2) + 4))} \\ &:= \frac{(31 + 5) \times 90}{7 \times (8 \times (6 \times 24))} := \frac{3 \times (1 + (59 - 0))}{7 \times (8 \times (6 - (2 - 4)))} := \frac{(3 - (1 - 5)) \times 90}{7 \times ((8 + 6) \times (2^4))} := \frac{(3 \times (1 + 5)) - (9 - 0)}{7 \times (8 + (62 \times 4))} \\ &:= \frac{315 - 90}{7 \times ((8 + (6 \times 2)) \times 4)} := \frac{3 \times ((1^5) \times 90)}{7 \times (8 \times (6 + (2 + 4)))} := \frac{(3 + (1 + 5)) \times 90}{7 \times (8 \times (6 \times (2 + 4)))} := \frac{((3 + 1)^5) \times 90}{7 \times (8 \times ((6 + 2)^4))} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (15 + 90)}{7 \times (8 \times (6 + (2 \times 4)))} := \frac{(3 - 1) \times (5 \times 90)}{7 \times (8 \times ((6^2) + 4))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{32784}{90156} &:= \frac{3 \times (2^{7-8+4})}{9 - (0 - (1 + 56))} := \frac{(3 - (2 - 7)) \times (8 - 4)}{(9 + (0 - 1)) \times (5 + 6)} := \frac{3 \times ((2 - (7 - 8)) \times 4)}{9 \times ((01 \times (5 + 6)))} := \frac{3 - (2 - (7 + (8 \times 4)))}{(9 - (0 - 1)) \times (5 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{3 + (2 + (7 + (8 \times 4)))}{90 + (1 + (5 \times 6))} := \frac{3 - (27 - 84)}{9 - (0 - 156)} := \frac{3 - (2 - (7 + (8 - 4)))}{9 + (0 - ((1 - 5) \times 6))} := \frac{(3 \times ((2^7) - 8)) + 4}{(90 + 1) \times (5 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{((3 \times 27) + 8) \times 4}{(90 - 1) \times (5 + 6)} := \frac{3 \times ((2 \times (7 \times 8)) + 4)}{901 + 56} := \frac{3 \times (2 \times ((7 + 8) \times 4))}{90 \times (1 \times (5 + 6))} := \frac{3 + (2 + (7 + (8 - 4)))}{((9 - (0 - 1)) \times 5) - 6} \\ &:= \frac{3 - (2 - (7 - (8 - 4)))}{9 - (0 - (1 - (5 - 6)))} := \frac{(32 + 7) \times 84}{9015 - 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{34510}{89726} &:= \frac{(3 + (4 - 5)) \times 10}{(8^9 - 7) - (2 \times 6)} := \frac{((3 + 4) \times 5) - 10}{8 - (9 - (72 - 6))} := \frac{3 \times (4 + (5 + (1 - 0)))}{(8 - (9 - (7 \times 2))) \times 6} := \frac{(3 + 4) \times (5 \times (1 - 0))}{((8 + 9) \times (7 - 2)) + 6} \\ &:= \frac{(3 - (4 - 5)) \times 10}{89 + (7 + (2 + 6))} := \frac{((3 + 4) \times 5) + 10}{8 + (97 + (2 \times 6))} := \frac{3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (1 - 0)))}{(8 + (9 + (7 + 2))) \times 6} := \frac{(3 + (4 + 5)) \times 10}{8 \times (9 + ((7 - 2) \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(34 \times 5) - 10}{8 \times (9 + ((7^2) - 6))} := \frac{(34 - 5) \times 10}{(8 \times (97 - 2)) - 6} := \frac{3 \times ((4 + 5) \times 10)}{(((8 + 9) \times 7) - 2) \times 6} := \frac{345 - 10}{897 - 26} \\ &:= \frac{345 + 10}{897 + 26} := \frac{(34 + 5) \times 10}{(8 \times (9 \times (7 \times 2))) + 6} := \frac{34 \times (5 + 10)}{(8 + 9) \times (72 + 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{35710}{92846} &:= \frac{3 + (5 + (7 - 10))}{9 - (2 - (8 + (4 - 6)))} := \frac{3 - (5 - (7 + 10))}{9 - (2 - (8 + (4 \times 6)))} := \frac{3 + (5 + (7 + 10))}{9 + (2 + (8 + 46))} := \frac{3 + (57 - 10)}{92 - (8 - 46)} \\ &:= \frac{3 + (57 + 10)}{92 + (84 + 6)} := \frac{3 \times (5 \times (7 - (1 - 0)))}{9 \times (2 + ((8 - 4) \times 6))} := \frac{3 \times (5 \times (7 \times (1 - 0)))}{(9^2) + (8 \times (4 \times 6))} := \frac{(3 \times (5 \times 7)) + 10}{9 + (284 + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{3 \times (5 \times (7 + (1 - 0)))}{(9 \times (2 + (8 \times 4))) + 6} := \frac{35 \times (7 - (1 - 0))}{(9 - (2 - 84)) \times 6} := \frac{(3 \times (5 + 7)) - (1 - 0)}{9 + (2 + (8 \times (4 + 6)))} := \frac{3 \times (5 + (7 \times 10))}{(9^2) + (84 \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(3^5) + (7 - 10)}{(92 + (8 + 4)) \times 6} := \frac{(3^5) + (7 \times (1 - 0))}{((9^2) \times 8) - (4 - 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{52630}{89471} &:= \frac{5 + ((2 \times 6) + (3 - 0))}{8 - ((9 \times (4 - 7)) + 1)} := \frac{5 \times (2 \times (6 - (3 - 0)))}{8 + ((9 \times 4) + (7 \times 1))} := \frac{5 + (2 + (63 - 0))}{(8 \times 9) + (47 \times 1)} := \frac{5 \times (2 + (6 \times (3 - 0)))}{(8 + 9) \times (4 + (7 - 1))} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times (2 \times (6 + 30))}{(8 + 94) \times (7 - 1)} := \frac{5 \times ((2 + 6) \times (3 - 0))}{(8 + 9) \times (4 + (7 + 1))} := \frac{(5 \times 26) + 30}{8 \times (((9 - 4) \times 7) - 1)} := \frac{5 \times (26 + 30)}{(8 + 9) \times (4 \times (7 \times 1))} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times ((2^6) + 30)}{(8 + 9) \times (47 \times 1)} := \frac{(5 - (2 - 6)) \times 30}{(8 + 9) \times ((4 \times 7) - 1)} := \frac{(5 \times (2^6)) - 30}{(8 + 9) \times ((4 \times 7) + 1)} := \frac{(5 \times (2^6)) + 30}{(89 - 4) \times (7 \times 1)} \\ &:= \frac{((5 \times 2) + 6) \times 30}{8 \times (94 + (7 + 1))} := \frac{5 \times (2^{6-3+0})}{(8 \times 9) + (4 - (7 + 1))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{53802}{69174} &:= \frac{(5 \times 3) - (8 - (0 \times 2))}{6 - (9 - (1 + (7 + 4)))} := \frac{5 + (3 + (8 + (0 - 2)))}{6 + (9 + (1 \times (7 - 4)))} := \frac{(5 \times 3) + (8 + (0 - 2))}{6 + (9 + (1 + (7 + 4)))} := \frac{((5 \times 3) - (8 - 0))^2}{(6 \times (9 + 1)) + (7 - 4)} \\ &:= \frac{(53 + 80) \times 2}{6 + ((91 - 7) \times 4)} := \frac{53 + (8 - (0 - 2))}{(6 - (9 + (1 - 7)))^4} := \frac{5 - (3 - (80 + 2))}{6 + (91 + (7 + 4))} := \frac{(5^3) + (8 - (0 \times 2))}{6 - (9 - 174)} \\ &:= \frac{5 + (3 + (80 \times 2))}{6 \times (9 \times (1 + (7 - 4)))} := \frac{(5^3) + (8^{02})}{69 + 174} := \frac{5 + (3 \times (8 - (0 - 2)))}{(6 + (9 \times 1)) \times (7 - 4)} := \frac{5 + ((3 + (8 - 0))^2)}{6 \times (9 \times (1 \times (7 - 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{5 \times (3 + 802)}{69 \times (1 + 74)} := \frac{(5 + 380) \times 2}{6 \times (91 + 74)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{65392}{81740} & := \frac{6 + ((5 + (3 - 9)) \times 2)}{8 - (1 \times (7 - (4 - 0)))} := \frac{6 - ((5 + (3 - 9)) \times 2)}{8 - (1 - (7 - (4 - 0)))} := \frac{6 - (5 + (3 - (9 \times 2)))}{8 + (1 + (7 + (4 - 0)))} := \frac{6 + ((5 - (3 - 9)) \times 2)}{8 - (1 - (7 \times (4 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{6 + (5 + (3 \times (9 - 2)))}{8 - (1 + (7 - 40))} := \frac{6 + (5 + ((3 \times 9) - 2))}{((8 - 1) \times 7) - (4 - 0)} := \frac{6 + (5 + (3 \times (9 + 2)))}{8 + (1 \times (7 + 40))} := \frac{6 + (5 + (39 - 2))}{(8 \times (1 + 7)) - (4 - 0)} \\ & := \frac{6 + (5 + (39 + 2))}{8 + (17 + 40)} := \frac{6 + (5 \times (3 + (9 - 2)))}{81 - (7 + (4 - 0))} := \frac{(6 - (5 - 39)) \times 2}{(8 + 17) \times (4 - 0)} := \frac{6 + ((5^3) - (9 - 2))}{81 + (74 - 0)} \\ & := \frac{6 \times (((5 \times 3) + 9) \times 2)}{(8 + (1^7)) \times 40} := \frac{(6 \times (5 - (3 - 9))) - 2}{(8 + (1 - 7)) \times 40} \end{aligned}$$

• **Four Digit's Numerator**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1803}{279465} & := \frac{((1^8 + 0) \times 3)}{(2 + (7 - (9 - 465)))} := \frac{((1^8 + 0) + 3)}{(2 \times ((7 + (9 + 46)) \times 5))} := \frac{((1 + (8 - 0)) \times 3)}{(279 \times (4 + (6 + 5)))} := \frac{((1 + (8 - 0))^3)}{(27 \times (9 \times 465))} \\ & := \frac{((1 + 80) \times 3)}{((2 + 79) \times 465)} := \frac{(1 \times (8 - (0 \times 3)))}{((2 + ((7 \times (9 \times 4)) - 6)) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 \times (8 + (0 - 3)))}{((2 \times (7 \times (9 + 46))) + 5)} := \frac{(1^{803})}{((2 + ((7 \times (9 - 4)) - 6)) \times 5)} \\ & := \frac{(1 + (8 - (0 \times 3)))}{((2 \times (7 \times (94 + 6))) - 5)} := \frac{(1 + (8 - (0 - 3)))}{((2 - (7 - 9)) \times 465)} := \frac{(1 + (8 + (0 - 3)))}{((2 - (7 - (9 \times 4))) \times (6 \times 5))} := \frac{(18 - (0 \times 3))}{((2 + (7 \times (9 + 4))) \times (6 \times 5))} \\ & := \frac{(18 \times (0 + 3))}{((2 + (7 + 9)) \times 465)} := \frac{(18 + (0 - 3))}{(((2 \times 7) - 9) \times 465)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1863}{279450} & := \frac{((1^{86}) \times 3)}{(2 + (7 - (9 - 450)))} := \frac{((1 + (8 + 6)) \times 3)}{(27 \times ((9 - 4) \times 50))} := \frac{(1 + 8) \times 63}{(2 + 7) \times 9450} := \frac{(1 + 8)^{6-3}}{(27 \times (9 \times 450))} \\ & := \frac{(1 \times ((8 - 6)^3))}{(2 \times ((7 + (9 - 4)) \times 50))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 - (6 - 3)))}{(2 \times ((79 - 4) \times (5 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (6 - 3)))}{((2 + (7 + 9)) \times (4 \times 50))} := \frac{(1 + ((8 - 6)^3))}{(((2 \times 7) + (9 + 4)) \times 50)} \\ & := \frac{(1 + (8 + (6 - 3)))}{((2 - (7 - 9)) \times 450)} := \frac{(18 - (6 - 3))}{((2 + (7 + (9 \times 4))) \times 50)} := \frac{(18 \times (6 \times 3))}{(27 \times (9 \times (4 \times 50)))} := \frac{(18 \times (6 - 3))}{(((2 \times 79) + 4) \times 50)} \\ & := \frac{(18 + (6 \times 3))}{(((2 \times 7) + 94) \times 50)} := \frac{(18 + (6 - 3))}{((27 + (9 \times 4)) \times 50)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1956}{273840} & := \frac{(((1^9) + 5) \times 6)}{((2 + (7 - 3)) \times 840)} := \frac{(((1 + 9) \times 5) - 6)}{(2 \times (7 \times ((3 + 8) \times 40)))} := \frac{((1^9) - (5 - 6))}{(2 \times (7 \times ((3 \times 8) - (4 - 0))))} := \frac{((1^9) + (5 + 6))}{(2 \times ((7 + 3) \times (84 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{((19 + 5) \times 6)}{((27 - 3) \times 840)} := \frac{(1 - (9 - 56))}{(2 \times ((7 - 3) \times 840))} := \frac{(1 \times (9 - (5 - 6)))}{(((2 + 7) \times 3) + 8) \times 40} := \frac{(1 \times (9 + (5 + 6)))}{(((2 + (7^3)) \times 8) + 40)} \\ & := \frac{(1 \times (9 + (5 - 6)))}{(((2 \times (7 + 3)) + 8) \times 40)} := \frac{1^{956}}{((2^7) + (3 \times (8 - (4 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 + (9 + 56))}{(((2 \times 7) - 3) \times 840)} := \frac{(1 + (95 + 6))}{(((2 \times 7) + 3) \times 840)} \\ & := \frac{(19 + (5 - 6))}{((27 + 3) \times (84 - 0))} := \frac{(19 + 56)}{(((2^7) - 3) \times (84 - 0))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{2439}{175608} & := \frac{(((2 + 4)^3) + 9)}{(1 + ((7^5) - 608))} := \frac{((2 - (4 - 3)) \times 9)}{(1 \times ((75 + (6 - 0)) \times 8))} := \frac{((2 \times (4 \times 3)) - 9)}{(1 \times ((75 + 60) \times 8))} := \frac{((2 + (4 + 3)) \times 9)}{(((1 + (7 - 5))^6 + 0) \times 8)} \\ & := \frac{(2 - ((4 - 3)^9))}{(((1 + (7 - (5 - (6 - 0)))) \times 8)} := \frac{(2 - (4 \times (3 - 9)))}{((1 + (7 \times 5)) \times (60 - 8))} := \frac{(2 - (4 + (3 - 9)))}{((1 - (7 + (5 \times 6))) \times (0 - 8))} := \frac{(2 \times (4 - (3 - 9)))}{(((1 + (7 - 5)) \times (60 \times 8))} \\ & := \frac{(2^{4 \times 3 - 9})}{(1 \times ((7 + (5 + 60)) \times 8))} := \frac{(2^{(4-3)^9})}{(1 \times ((7 + (5 + (6 - 0))) \times 8))} := \frac{(2 + ((4 - 3)^9))}{((1 + (7 \times 5)) \times (6 - (0 \times 8)))} := \frac{(2 + (4 \times (3 + 9)))}{(1 \times (75 \times (6 \times (0 + 8))))} \\ & := \frac{(24 \times (3 \times 9))}{(((1^7) + 5)^{6+0 \times 8})} := \frac{(24 + 39)}{(1 \times ((7 + 560) \times 8))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4032}{197568} &:= \frac{((4 - (0 - 3)) \times 2)}{(1 + ((9 \times (7 \times (5 + 6))) - 8))} := \frac{((4 + (0 - 3)) \times 2)}{(1 \times (9 + (75 + (6 + 8))))} := \frac{((4 + (0 - 3))^2)}{(1 - (9 + (7 - (56 + 8))))} := \frac{(4 - ((0 \times 3) - 2))}{(1 \times ((9 + (7 + 5)) \times (6 + 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - (0 - (3 \times 2)))}{((1^9) \times (7 \times (5 \times (6 + 8))))} := \frac{(4 - (0 - (3 + 2)))}{(1 \times (9 \times (7 \times (5 - (6 - 8)))))} := \frac{(4 - (0 - (3 - 2)))}{(((1 + (9 - 7))^5) - (6 - 8))} := \frac{(4 - (0 \times 32))}{((19 \times 7) - (5 - 68))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times ((0 \times 3) + 2))}{(1 - (9 - ((7 \times 56) + 8)))} := \frac{(4 \times (0 + (3 \times 2)))}{(1 \times ((9 + 75) \times (6 + 8)))} := \frac{(4 \times (0 + 32))}{((1 + 97) \times (56 + 8))} := \frac{(4^{0 \times 3 + 2})}{(1 \times ((97 - (5 - 6)) \times 8))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (0 - (3 - 2)))}{(1 + ((9 - 7) \times (5 + 68)))} := \frac{(40 + 32)}{((1 - 9) \times (7 \times (5 - 68)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{5697}{182304} &:= \frac{((5 - (6 - 9))^7)}{(1 \times ((8^{2^3+0}) \times 4))} := \frac{((5 \times (6 + 9)) - 7)}{(1 \times ((8^2) \times (30 + 4)))} := \frac{((5 \times 6) + (9 - 7))}{(1 \times (8 \times (2^{3+04})))} := \frac{((5 + (6 - 9)) \times 7)}{(1 \times (8 \times ((2 \times 30) - 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{((5 + (6 - 9))^7)}{1 \times 8^{2^3} - 04} := \frac{(5 - (6 - (9 - 7)))}{(1 \times (8 - (2 \times (3 \times (0 - 4)))))} := \frac{(5 \times (6 \times (9 - 7)))}{(1 \times (8 \times (2 \times (30 \times 4))))} := \frac{(5 + ((6 \times 9) - 7))}{(1 \times ((8^2) \times (30 - 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + (6 - (9 - 7)))}{(1 \times (8 \times (2 + (30 + 4))))} := \frac{(5 + (6 \times (9 - 7)))}{(1 \times (8 \times (2 \times (30 + 4))))} := \frac{(5 + (6 + (9 + 7)))}{(1 \times (((8 - 2)^3 + 0) \times 4))} := \frac{(5 + (6 + (9 - 7)))}{(1 \times (8 \times (2 \times (30 - 4))))} \\ &:= \frac{(56 + (9 + 7))}{(18 \times (2^{3+04}))} := \frac{(569 + 7)}{(1 \times (8 \times 2304))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{5697}{341820} &:= \frac{((5 \times (6 + 9)) + 7)}{((3 + (4 - 1)) \times 820)} := \frac{((5 \times 6) + (9 - 7))}{(3 \times (4 \times (1 \times (8 \times 20))))} := \frac{((5 + (6 - 9)) \times 7)}{((34 + (1 \times 8)) \times 20)} := \frac{((5 + 6) \times (9 - 7))}{(3 \times ((4 + 18) \times 20))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 - (6 - (9 + 7)))}{((3^4) - (1 - 820))} := \frac{(5 - (6 - (9 - 7)))}{(3 \times (4 + (1 \times (8 \times (2 - 0)))))} := \frac{(5 \times ((6 + 9)^7))}{(((3 \times (4 + 1))^8) \times 20)} := \frac{(5 \times (6 + (9 - 7)))}{(3 \times ((4 + 1) \times (8 \times 20)))} \\ &:= \frac{(5^{6+9-7})}{(3 \times (((4 + 1)^8) \times 20))} := \frac{(5 + (6 - (9 - 7)))}{((3^4 - 1^8) \times 20)} := \frac{(5 + (6 + (9 + 7)))}{3^4 \times 1^8 \times 20} := \frac{(5 + (6 + (9 - 7)))}{(3 \times (4 \times (1 + (8^2 + 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + (69 + 7))}{((3^4 + 1^8) \times 20)} := \frac{(56 + (9 + 7))}{(3 \times (4 \times (18 \times 20)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{6489}{175203} &:= \frac{(((6 \times 4) + 8) \times 9)}{(((1^7) + 5)^{2+03})} := \frac{(((6 - 4) \times 8) - 9)}{(1 \times (7 \times ((5 - (2 - 0))^3)))} := \frac{(((6 + (4 - 8))^9))}{(1 \times (((7 + 5) \times (2 - 0))^3))} := \frac{(((6 - 4) \times (8 \times 9))}{(((1 + (7 \times 5))^2 + 0) \times 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - (4 - (8 - 9)))}{((1 - (7 + (5 - 20))) \times 3)} := \frac{(6 - (4 \times (8 - 9)))}{((1 - 7) \times ((5 - 20) \times 3))} := \frac{(6 - (4 + (8 - 9)))}{(1 + (75 + (2 - (0 - 3))))} := \frac{(6 \times (4 \times (8 \times 9)))}{(((1^7) + 5)^{2 \times 03})} \\ &:= \frac{(6^{4+8-9})}{(((1 + (7 + (5 \times (2 - 0))))^3)} := \frac{(6 + (4 \times (8 - 9)))}{(((1 + (7 + (5 \times (2 - 0)))) \times 3)} := \frac{(6 + (4 + (8 + 9)))}{((1 - (7 + (5 - 20)))^3)} := \frac{(6 + (4 + (8 - 9)))}{((1 + (7 - 5))^2 + 03)} \\ &:= \frac{(64 - (8 - 9))}{(1752 - (0 - 3))} := \frac{(64 + (8 \times 9))}{((1 - ((7 \times 5)^2)) \times (0 - 3))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{7203}{468195} &:= \frac{((7 \times (2 - 0)) - 3)}{(((4 + 68) \times (1 + 9)) - 5)} := \frac{((7^2 + 0) + 3)}{((4 + (681 - 9)) \times 5)} := \frac{((7 + (2 - 0)) \times 3)}{((46 - (8 - 1)) \times (9 \times 5))} := \frac{(7 - (2 - (0 \times 3)))}{(((4 \times (6 + (8 \times 1))) + 9) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(7 - (2 - (0 - 3)))}{(4 + (6 \times (8 - (1 - (9 + 5)))))} := \frac{(7 - (2 \times (0 \times 3)))}{((4 + (6 + ((8 + 1) \times 9))) \times 5)} := \frac{(7 - (2 + (0 - 3)))}{(4 - (6 \times (8 + (1 - 95))))} := \frac{(7 \times (2 - (0 \times 3)))}{(((4 \times (6 \times 8)) - (1 + 9)) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + (2 - (0 \times 3)))}{(4 + ((6 \times 81) + 95))} := \frac{(7 + (2 - (0 - 3)))}{(4 \times (((6 \times (8 \times 1)) - 9) \times 5))} := \frac{(7 + (2 \times (0 - 3)))}{(4 + (6 - ((8 - 19) \times 5)))} := \frac{(7 + (2 + (0 - 3)))}{((4 - (6 - (8 \times (1 + 9)))) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + (20 - 3))}{(4 \times ((6 + (8 \times (1 \times 9))) \times 5))} := \frac{(72 \times (0 + 3))}{((4 + 68) \times 195)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{7418}{259630} &:= \frac{((7 - (4 \times 1)) \times 8)}{(2 \times (5 \times ((9 \times 6) + 30)))} := \frac{((7 \times (4 \times 1)) + 8)}{(2 \times (5 \times (96 + 30)))} := \frac{((7 + (4 + 1)) \times 8)}{(((2 \times 59) - 6) \times 30)} := \frac{((7 + 4) \times 18)}{(((25 \times 9) + 6) \times 30)} \\ &:= \frac{((7 - 4) \times 18)}{(2 \times (5 \times (9 + (6 \times 30))))} := \frac{(7 - (4 \times (1^8)))}{((2 \times ((5 \times 9) + 6)) + (3 - 0))} := \frac{(7 - (4 + (1^8)))}{((2 \times (5 + (9 + 6))) + 30)} := \frac{(7 \times (4 \times (1 + 8)))}{(((2^5) \times 9) + 6) \times 30)} \\ &:= \frac{(7 \times (4 \times 18))}{(2 \times ((5 + 9) \times 630))} := \frac{(7 + ((4 + 1) \times 8))}{(25 + (9 \times (6 \times 30)))} := \frac{(7 + (4 - (1 - 8)))}{((2 + 5) \times ((9 - 6) \times 30))} := \frac{(74 - (1 \times 8))}{((2 + (5 \times (9 + 6))) \times 30)} \\ &:= \frac{(74 \times 18)}{(259 \times (6 \times 30))} := \frac{(74 + (1 + 8))}{(25 + (96 \times 30))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7915}{348260} &:= \frac{((7 \times (9 \times 1)) + 5)}{(34 \times (82 + (6 - 0)))} &:= \frac{((7 \times (9 - 1)) - 5)}{(34 \times (8 - (2 - 60)))} &:= \frac{((7 \times 9) - (1^5))}{((34 \times 82) - 60)} &:= \frac{((7 - 9) \times (1 - 5))}{(348 - (2 - (6 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 - (9 - (1 \times 5)))}{((3 \times (4 \times (8 - 2))) + 60)} &:= \frac{(7 - (9 - (1 + 5)))}{(34 + (82 + 60))} &:= \frac{(7 - (9 + (1 - 5)))}{((3 \times (4 \times 8)) - (2 + (6 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(7 \times (9 - (1 + 5)))}{((3 \times (4 \times 82)) - 60)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (9 - (1 \times 5)))}{((34 \times (8 \times 2)) - 60)} &:= \frac{(7 + (9 - (1^5)))}{((3 - ((4 - 8) \times 2)) \times 60)} &:= \frac{(7 + (9 + (1^5)))}{(34 \times (82 - 60))} &:= \frac{(7 + (9 + (1 - 5)))}{(((3^4) \times 8) - (2 \times 60))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (9 - 15))}{((3 \times (4 + 8)) + (2 + (6 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(79 \times (1^5))}{(3482 - (6 - 0))} && \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7961}{350284} &:= \frac{((7 \times 9) - 61)}{(((3 \times (5 \times (0 + 2))) - 8) \times 4)} &:= \frac{((7 + 9) \times (6 \times 1))}{((350 + 2) \times (8 + 4))} &:= \frac{(7 - (9 - (6 \times 1)))}{(3 + (5 - (0 - (2 \times 84))))} &:= \frac{(7 - (9 - (6 + 1)))}{(((3^5 - 0^2) \times 8) + 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 - (9 - (6 - 1)))}{(3 \times ((5 + (0 - (2 - 8))) \times 4))} &:= \frac{(7 \times (9 - (6 + 1)))}{((350 \times 2) - 84)} &:= \frac{(7 \times (9 - (6 - 1)))}{(((3 \times (50 \times 2)) + 8) \times 4)} &:= \frac{(7 \times (9 + (6 \times 1)))}{((3 + (50 + 2)) \times 84)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 \times (96 \times 1))}{((350 + 2) \times 84)} &:= \frac{(7 + (9 - (6 + 1)))}{(3 \times ((5 - (0 - 28)) \times 4))} &:= \frac{(7 + (9 + (6 + 1)))}{(((3^5 + 0) + (2 + 8)) \times 4)} &:= \frac{(79 - (6 \times 1))}{((3 + (50 \times (2 \times 8))) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(796 \times 1)}{(35028 - 4)} &:= \frac{(79 - 61)}{(3 \times ((50 + (2 \times 8)) \times 4))} && \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{8307}{149526} &:= \frac{((8 \times (3 - 0)) - 7)}{(1 \times ((4 + ((9 \times 5) + 2)) \times 6))} &:= \frac{((8 + (3 - 0)) \times 7)}{(14 \times (95 - (2 - 6)))} &:= \frac{(8 - (3 - (0 \times 7)))}{((1 + ((4 \times (9 - 5)) - 2)) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(8 - (3 \times (0 \times 7)))}{(1 + (4 + (9 + (5 \times 26))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 - (3 \times (0 - 7)))}{(1 + (4 - (9 - 526)))} &:= \frac{(8 - (3 + (0 - 7)))}{(1 - (4 - ((9 \times (5^2)) - 6)))} &:= \frac{(8 \times (3 - (0 \times 7)))}{(1 + (495 - (2^6)))} &:= \frac{(8 \times (3 - (0 - 7)))}{(1 \times (4 \times (9 \times (5 \times (2 + 6)))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8^{3+0 \times 7})}{((149 - 5) \times (2^6))} &:= \frac{(8 + (3 - (0 \times 7)))}{((1 + (4 \times ((9 - 5) \times 2))) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(8 + (3 - (0 - 7)))}{(1 \times (4 \times (9 \times (5 - (2 - 6)))))} &:= \frac{(8 + (3 + (0 - 7)))}{(1 \times (4 + (9 - (5 - (2^6)))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 + (30 + 7))}{((1 + 4) \times (9 \times ((5 - 2) \times 6)))} &:= \frac{(8 + (30 - 7))}{((1^4) \times ((95 - 2) \times 6))} && \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{8307}{465192} &:= \frac{((8 - (3 - 0)) \times 7)}{((4 + 6) \times ((5 + (1 \times 9))^2))} &:= \frac{((8 \times (3 - 0)) - 7)}{(((4 + 6) \times (5 \times 19)) + 2)} &:= \frac{(8 - (3 - (0 \times 7)))}{(4 \times ((6 + (5 - 1)) \times (9 - 2)))} &:= \frac{(8 - (3 \times (0 \times 7)))}{(4 \times ((6 + (5 \times (1 + 9))) \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 - (3 \times (0 - 7)))}{(4 \times (6 - (5 \times (1 - (9^2)))))} &:= \frac{(8 - (3 + (0 - 7)))}{(4 \times (6 \times ((5 + (1 \times 9)) \times 2)))} &:= \frac{(8 \times (3 - (0 \times 7)))}{(4 \times (6 \times (((5 + 1) \times 9) + 2)))} &:= \frac{(8^{3+0 \times 7})}{((4^6) \times (5 + ((1^9) \times 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 + (3 - (0 - 7)))}{(4 \times (6 \times ((5 + 1) \times (9 - 2))))} &:= \frac{(8 + (3 + (0 - 7)))}{(4 \times (6 - (5 \times (1 - (9 + 2)))))} &:= \frac{(8 + (30 + 7))}{(4 \times (6 \times (5 \times (19 + 2))))} &:= \frac{(8 + 307)}{((4 + 6) \times ((51 - 9)^2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(83 - (0 \times 7))}{((465 \times (1 + 9)) - 2)} &:= \frac{(830 + 7)}{(4 \times (651 \times (9 \times 2)))} && \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{8406}{273195} &:= \frac{((8 - (4 - 0)) \times 6)}{((2 + (7 \times (3 + 19))) \times 5)} &:= \frac{((8 \times (4 - 0)) + 6)}{((2 + (7 + (3 + 1))) \times 95)} &:= \frac{((8 + (4 - 0)) \times 6)}{((2 + (7 + 3)) \times 195)} &:= \frac{(8 - (4 - (0 \times 6)))}{(2 - (7 - (3 \times (1 \times (9 \times 5)))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 - (4 \times (0 \times 6)))}{((2 - (7 - (3 \times 19))) \times 5)} &:= \frac{(8 - (4 + (0 - 6)))}{(((2 \times (7 \times (3 + 1))) + 9) \times 5)} &:= \frac{(8 + (4 - (0 \times 6)))}{(2 + ((7^3 \times 1) + (9 \times 5)))} &:= \frac{(8 + (4 - (0 - 6)))}{((2 + (7 + (3 + 1))) \times (9 \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 + (4 + (0 - 6)))}{((2 + (7 + (3 \times (1 + 9)))) \times 5)} &:= \frac{(8 + (40 + 6))}{(27 \times ((3 + (1 + 9)) \times 5))} &:= \frac{(8 + (40 - 6))}{(273 \times (1 + (9 - 5)))} &:= \frac{(84 - (0 \times 6))}{(((2 \times 7)^3 \times 1) - (9 + 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(84 \times (0 + 6))}{(((2^7)^{3-1}) - (9 - 5))} &:= \frac{(84 + (0 - 6))}{((2 - (7 - ((3 - 1)^9))) \times 5)} &&
 \end{aligned}$$

3.14 15 Equivalent Blocks

- Five Digit's Numerator

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10392}{67548} &:= \frac{((1 - (0 - (3 \times 9))) \times 2)}{((6 + 7) \times ((5 \times 4) + 8))} := \frac{((1^{03}) \times (9 \times 2))}{((6 + 7) \times (5 - (4 - 8)))} := \frac{((1^{03}) \times 92)}{((6 + 7) \times (54 - 8))} \\ &:= \frac{((10 + (3 \times 9)) \times 2)}{((6 + 7) \times (5 + (4 \times 8)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - ((3 \times 9) + 2)))}{(6 - (7 \times (5 - (4 \times 8))))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (3 \times (9 + 2))))}{((6 + 7) \times (5 + (4 + 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times ((0 - (3 - 9))^2))}{(6 \times ((7 \times 5) - (4 - 8)))} := \frac{(1 \times ((0 \times 39) + 2))}{(6 + (7^{5+4-8}))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 - (3 - (9 + 2))))}{(6 - (7 - (5 + 48)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 - (3 - (9 - 2))))}{(6 - (7 + (5 - (4 \times 8))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((3 + 9) \times 2)))}{(((6 + (7 \times 5)) \times 4) - 8)} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((3 + 9)^2))}{((6 + 7) \times ((5 + 4) \times 8))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (3 - (9 \times 2))))}{((6 + (7 \times (5 - 4))) \times 8)} := \frac{(10 + (3 - (9 - 2)))}{(67 - ((5 \times 4) + 8))} := \frac{(10 + (3 + (9^2)))}{((67 \times (5 + 4)) + 8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10968}{34275} &:= \frac{(((1^{09}) + 6) \times 8)}{((3 + (4 - 2)) \times (7 \times 5))} := \frac{((1 - (0 - (9 - 6))) \times 8)}{((3 \times (42 - 7)) - 5)} := \frac{((1^{09}) \times (6 \times 8))}{(((3^4) \times 2) - (7 + 5))} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + (0 - 9)) \times (6 - 8))}{((3 \times (4^2)) + (7 - 5))} := \frac{((109 - 6) \times 8)}{((3 + (4 \times (2^7))) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 + (6 + 8))))}{((3 - (4 - 2)) \times 75)} \\ &:= \frac{((3 + (4 - 2))^{7-5})}{(1 \times (0 + (96 \times 8)))} := \frac{(3 + (4 - 2)) \times 75}{(1 \times (0 + ((9 + 6) \times 8)))} := \frac{(3 \times ((4 + 2) \times 75))}{(1 \times (0 + (9 \times (6 \times 8))))} \\ &:= \frac{((34 - 2) \times 75)}{(10 \times ((9 - 6) \times 8))} := \frac{(((3 \times (4^2)) + 7) \times 5)}{(10 + ((9 \times 6) + 8))} := \frac{(((3 \times (4 + 2)) + 7) \times 5)}{(10 + (9 \times (6 + 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{((3 \times 4) - 2) \times 75}{((3 + ((4 + 2) \times 7)) \times 5)} := \frac{(3 + (427 - 5))}{((3 + (4 + 2) \times 7)) \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{12345}{98760} &:= \frac{(((1 - (2 - 3)) \times 4)^5)}{(9 - (8 - 7))^6 + 0} := \frac{((1 + 2) \times (34 + 5))}{(9 \times (8 \times (7 + (6 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 - (2 - ((3^4) - 5)))}{((9 + (8 - 7)) \times 60)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (2 \times (3 - 45)))}{((98 \times 7) - (6 - 0))} := \frac{(1 - (2 + (3 \times (4 - 5))))}{(9 + (8 - (7 - (6 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 \times (((2^3) + 4) \times 5))}{((9 - (8 - 7)) \times 60)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times ((2^3) \times (4 + 5)))}{((9 + 87) \times (6 - 0))} := \frac{(1 \times ((2 + 34) \times 5))}{((9 + (8 + 7)) \times 60)} := \frac{(1 \times ((23 - 4) \times 5))}{((9 - 8) \times 760)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (2 + (3 - (4 - 5))))}{((9 - (8 - 7)) \times (6 - 0))} := \frac{1^{2345}}{(9 - ((8 - 7)^6 + 0))} := \frac{(1 + ((2^3) + (4 + 5)))}{((9 + (8 + 7)) \times (6 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (2 \times (3 - (4 - 5))))}{9 \times 8^{7-6+0}} := \frac{(1 + (2 + (3 - (4 - 5))))}{(98 - (7 \times (6 - 0)))} := \frac{(12 \times (3 \times (4 \times 5)))}{((9 + 87) \times 60)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{13208}{75946} &:= \frac{(((1^3) + 20) \times 8)}{((7 + (5 + 9)) \times 46)} := \frac{((1 - (3 - 20)) \times 8)}{((7 - 5) \times (9 \times 46))} := \frac{((1^3) \times (20 + 8))}{(7 \times (5 - (9 \times (4 - 6))))} \\ &:= \frac{((1^3) \times (20 - 8))}{(7 + (((5 + 9) \times 4) + 6))} := \frac{((13 - (2 - 0)) \times 8)}{((7 - (5 - 9)) \times 46)} := \frac{(1 - (3 - (2 - (0 - 8))))}{((7 \times 5) + (9 - (4 - 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (3 + (2 + (0 - 8))))}{(7 + (5 + (9 - (4 - 6))))} := \frac{(1 \times ((3 \times 20) + 8))}{((7 \times (59 - 4)) + 6)} := \frac{(1 \times (3 \times (20 + 8)))}{(7 + ((5 \times 94) + 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (32 + (0 - 8)))}{((7 - ((5 - 9) \times 4)) \times 6)} := \frac{(1 + (3 - (2 \times (0 - 8))))}{(7 + ((5 + (9 + 4)) \times 6))} := \frac{(1 + (3 + (20 - 8)))}{(7 - (5 - (9 \times (4 + 6))))} \\ &:= \frac{(13 \times (2 \times (0 + 8)))}{(((7 \times 5) - 9) \times 46)} := \frac{132 + 08}{759 + 46} := \frac{132 - 08}{759 - 46} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14607}{38952} &:= \frac{((1 - (4 - (6 - 0))) \times 7)}{(3 - (8 - (9 + 52)))} := \frac{((1 - (4 - (6 - 0)))^7)}{((3^8) - (9^{5-2}))} := \frac{((1 - (4 - 60)) \times 7)}{(38 \times ((9 + 5) \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{((1^4) \times (6 \times (0 + 7)))}{((3 + (8 + (9 \times 5))) \times 2)} := \frac{((1 + 4) \times (6 - (0 \times 7)))}{((3 - (8 - (9 \times 5))) \times 2)} := \frac{(1 - ((4 - (6 - 0)) \times 7))}{(3 + (89 - 52))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (4 + (6 \times (0 - 7))))}{(3 + (8 + (95 - 2)))} := \frac{(1 \times (4 \times (6 - (0 \times 7))))}{((3 \times (8 + (9 + 5))) - 2)} := \frac{(1 \times (4 + (6 + (0 - 7))))}{((3 + (8 - 9))^{5-2})} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 + (60 - 7)))}{(((3 + 8) \times (9 + 5)) - 2)} := \frac{(1 + (4 - (6 + (0 - 7))))}{((3 - ((8 - 9) \times 5)) \times 2)} := \frac{(1 + (4 + (6 - (0 - 7))))}{(3 \times (8 \times (9 - (5 + 2))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (4 + (60 + 7)))}{(3 \times (8^{9-5-2}))} := \frac{(1 + (46 - (0 - 7)))}{(3 \times (8 \times (9 - (5 - 2))))} := \frac{(14 + (6 - (0 - 7)))}{(3 + (8 + (9 + 52)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{15430}{67892} &:= \frac{(((1^5) + 4) \times 30)}{(678 - (9 \times 2))} := \frac{((1 + 54) \times (3 - 0))}{(6 \times ((7 \times (8 + 9)) + 2))} := \frac{(1 - (5 - (4 + 30)))}{(6 \times (7 + (8 + (9 - 2))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times ((5 \times 4) + 30))}{((6 \times 7) + (89 \times 2))} := \frac{(1 \times (5 \times (4 + (3 - 0))))}{(6 + ((7 \times 8) + 92))} := \frac{(1 \times (5^{4-3+0}))}{(6 + ((7 - (8 - 9)) \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (5 + (4 \times 30)))}{(((6 \times 7) + 8) \times (9 + 2))} := \frac{(1 + (5 + (4^3 + 0)))}{(((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9) + 2)} := \frac{(1 + (5 + (4 + 30)))}{((6 - (7 - 89)) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (54 + 30))}{(((6 \times 7) - 8) \times (9 + 2))} := \frac{(15 \times (4 \times 30))}{(6 - (7 - (89^2)))} := \frac{(15 \times (4^3 + 0))}{(6 \times ((78 \times 9) + 2))} \\ &:= \frac{(15 \times (4 + (3 - 0)))}{(6 \times (7 + ((8 \times 9) - 2)))} := \frac{(15^{4-3+0})}{(6 + (78 - (9 \times 2)))} := \frac{(15 + (4 \times 30))}{(6 - (7 \times (8 - 92)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{16470}{39528} &:= \frac{(((1 - 6) \times 4) + 70)}{((3 + (9 + (5 - 2))) \times 8)} := \frac{((1^6) \times (4 \times 70))}{(3 \times ((9 + 5) \times (2 \times 8)))} := \frac{((1^6) \times 470)}{(3 \times (((9 \times 5) + 2) \times 8))} \\ &:= \frac{((1^6) + (4 + 70))}{((3 - 9) \times (5 \times (2 - 8)))} := \frac{((1 + (6 \times 4)) \times (7 - 0))}{(3 \times ((9 + 5) \times (2 + 8)))} := \frac{((1 + 6) \times (4 \times 70))}{(3 \times (((9 + 5)^2) \times 8))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times ((6 + 4) \times 70))}{((3 + 9) \times (5 \times 28))} := \frac{(1 \times ((6 - 4) \times 70))}{(3 \times ((9 - 5) \times 28))} := \frac{(1 \times (6 + (4 + 70)))}{(3 + (9 \times (5 + (2 \times 8))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (64 \times 70))}{(3 \times ((9 + 5) \times (2^8)))} := \frac{(1 + ((6 - 4) \times (7 - 0)))}{(3 + (9 + ((5 - 2) \times 8)))} := \frac{(1 + (6 - (4 - (7 - 0))))}{(3 \times (9 + (5 + (2 - 8))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (6 + (4 \times (7 - 0))))}{(3 + (9^{5 \times 2 - 8}))} := \frac{(16 - (4 + (7 - 0)))}{(3 - (9 \times (5 + (2 - 8))))} := \frac{(16 + (4 + 70))}{((3 + 9) \times ((5 \times 2) + 8))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{16530}{42978} &:= \frac{(((1 + 6) \times 5) + 30)}{(4 + ((2 + 9) \times (7 + 8)))} := \frac{((1^6) \times (5 \times 30))}{((4 + 2) \times (9 + (7 \times 8)))} := \frac{((1 + 6) \times (5 \times 30))}{(42 \times (9 + (7 \times 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{((16 \times 5) - 30)}{(4 - (2 - ((9 + 7) \times 8)))} := \frac{(1 - (6 - (5 \times (3 - 0))))}{(4 - (2 - (9 + (7 + 8))))} := \frac{(1 - (6 - (5 \times 30)))}{((42 \times 9) + (7 - 8))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (6 - (5 + 30)))}{(4 + ((2 \times 9) + (7 \times 8)))} := \frac{(1 - (6 + (5 - 30)))}{(4 + (2 \times (9 + (7 + 8))))} := \frac{(1 \times ((6 + 5) \times 30))}{((4 - (2 - 9)) \times 78)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (6 \times (5^3 + 0)))}{(((4^2) + 9) \times 78)} := \frac{(1 \times (6 \times (5 + 30)))}{(42 + (9 \times (7 \times 8)))} := \frac{(1 \times (65 \times (3 - 0)))}{(429 + 78)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (65 - 30))}{(4 - (2 - (97 - 8)))} := \frac{(1 + (6 + (5 + (3 - 0))))}{(((4 + 2) \times 9) - (7 + 8))} := \frac{(165 - 30)}{(429 - 78)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{17805}{46293} &:= \frac{((1 - (7 + 8)) \times (0 - 5))}{((4 - 6) \times (2 - 93))} := \frac{((1^7) \times (8 \times (0 + 5)))}{((46 \times 2) + (9 + 3))} := \frac{((1^7) \times (80 + 5))}{((4 \times 62) - (9 \times 3))} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + (7 \times (8 - 0))) \times 5)}{(4 + (6 + (2 + (9^3))))} := \frac{((1 + 7) \times (80 - 5))}{((4 \times 6) + ((2^9) \times 3))} := \frac{((17 - (8 - 0)) \times 5)}{((4 + (6 + 29)) \times 3)} \\ &:= \frac{((1 - 7) \times (8 \times (0 - 5)))}{(4 \times (6 \times (29 - 3)))} := \frac{((17 + (8 - 0)) \times 5)}{(4 + (((6^2) \times 9) - 3))} := \frac{(1 \times ((7 + (8 - 0)) \times 5))}{(((4 \times 6) - 2) \times 9) - 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (7 + (8 - (0 \times 5))))}{(4 + (6 + (2 + (9 \times 3))))} := \frac{(1 \times (7 + (8 - (0 - 5))))}{(4 + (6 \times (2 + (9 - 3))))} := \frac{(1 \times (7 + (8 + (0 - 5))))}{((4 \times (6 + 2)) - (9 - 3))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (7 - (8 + (0 - 5))))}{(4 - (6 - ((2 \times 9) - 3)))} := \frac{(17 + (8 - (0 \times 5)))}{((4 \times (6 + (2 + 9))) - 3)} := \frac{(17 + (8 - (0 - 5)))}{(4 + (62 + (9 + 3)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{18354}{20976} &:= \frac{(((1 + (8 + 3)) \times 5) - 4)}{(2^{0 \times 97 + 6})} := \frac{((1 - (8 - 35)) \times 4)}{(2 \times (0 + ((9 - 7)^6)))} := \frac{((1 + ((8 + 3) \times 5)) \times 4)}{2^{09 - 7 + 6}} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + (8 + (3 - 5))) \times 4)}{(20 + ((9 - 7) \times 6))} := \frac{((1 + 83) \times (5 \times 4))}{(20 \times ((9 + 7) \times 6))} := \frac{((18 \times (3 + 5)) - 4)}{(20 \times (9 - (7 - 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{((18 + 3) \times (5 + 4))}{((20 + (9 + 7)) \times 6)} := \frac{((18 + 3) \times 54)}{((209 + 7) \times 6)} := \frac{(1 - (8 - (35 \times 4)))}{(2 \times ((0 \times 9) + 76))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times ((8^3) - (5 - 4)))}{(2 - (0 - (97 \times 6)))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 - (3 - (5 + 4))))}{(2 \times (0 + (9 - (7 - 6))))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (35 \times 4)))}{(20 \times ((9 - 7)^6))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (8 - (3 - (5 - 4))))}{(2 \times (0 - (9 - (7 + 6))))} := \frac{(1 + (8 + (3 + (5 + 4))))}{(2 - (0 - (9 + (7 + 6))))} := \frac{(183 - (5 - 4))}{(209 - (7 - 6))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{20853}{71496} &:= \frac{((2 - ((0 \times 8) - 5)) \times 3)}{(7 + (1 + (4^{9 - 6})))} := \frac{((2 - (0 - (8 \times 5))) \times 3)}{((7 + (1^4)) \times (9 \times 6))} := \frac{((2 \times ((0 \times 8) + 5)) - 3)}{(7 + (14 + (9 - 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{((2 \times (0 + (8 \times 5))) - 3)}{((7 + (1 + (4 \times 9))) \times 6)} := \frac{((2^{0 \times 8 + 5}) + 3)}{((7 + (1 \times (4 + 9))) \times 6)} := \frac{((20 \times 8) + (5 \times 3))}{((7 - 1) \times (4 + 96))} \\ &:= \frac{((20 \times 8) + (5 + 3))}{((7 - (1^4)) \times 96)} := \frac{((20 + 8) \times (5 + 3))}{((7 + (1^4)) \times 96)} := \frac{((20 + 8) \times (5 - 3))}{((7 - (1 + 4)) \times 96)} \\ &:= \frac{((20 + 8)^{5 - 3})}{(7 \times (1 \times (4 \times 96)))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (8 + 53)))}{((7 - (1^4))^{9 - 6})} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (85 - 3)))}{((7 - (1 \times 4)) \times 96)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 - (8 - (5 \times 3))))}{((7 \times (1 - (4 - 9))) + 6)} := \frac{(20 + (8 \times (5 \times 3)))}{((7 + 1) \times (4 \times (9 + 6)))} := \frac{(208 + (5 - 3))}{((71 + 49) \times 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{30485}{79261} &:= \frac{(((3^{04}) - 8) \times 5)}{((79 \times (2 \times 6)) + 1)} := \frac{((3 - (0 - (4 \times 8))) \times 5)}{(7 \times (((9 + 2) \times 6) - 1))} := \frac{((3 - (0 - (4 + 8))) \times 5)}{(((7 + 9)^2) - 61)} \\ &:= \frac{((3 \times (0 \times 48)) + 5)}{(7 + (9 + (2 - (6 - 1))))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 + 4)) + (8 + 5))}{((7 \times (9 \times 2)) - 61)} := \frac{((3 + (0 - (4 - 8))) \times 5)}{(7 \times (9 - (2 - (6 \times 1))))} \\ &:= \frac{((30 \times 4) - (8 \times 5))}{((7 + 9) \times ((2 \times 6) + 1))} := \frac{((30 \times 4) + (8 \times 5))}{((7 + 9) \times (26 \times 1))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - ((4 \times 8) + 5)))}{(7 + (92 + (6 - 1)))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 - (0 - ((4 \times 8) - 5)))}{(7 + ((9 \times (2 + 6)) - 1))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (4 \times (8 + 5))))}{(79 + (2^6 \times 1))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (4 \times (8 - 5))))}{(((7 + 9) \times 2) + (6 + 1))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 - (0 - (4 + (8 + 5))))}{(7 - (9 \times (2 - (6 + 1))))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (4 + (8 - 5))))}{(7 + (9 + (2 \times (6 - 1))))} := \frac{(30 + (4 \times (8 \times 5)))}{(7 + (((9^2) \times 6) + 1))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{34510}{89726} &:= \frac{(((3+4) \times 5) + 10)}{(8 + (97 + (2 \times 6)))} := \frac{(((3+4) \times 5) - 10)}{(8 - (9 - (72 - 6)))} := \frac{((3 - (4 - 5)) \times 10)}{(89 + (7 + (2 + 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 + (4 + 5)) \times 10)}{(8 \times (9 + ((7 - 2) \times 6)))} := \frac{((3 + (4 - 5)) \times 10)}{((8^{9-7}) - (2 \times 6))} := \frac{((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (1 - 0)))}{((8 + 9) \times (7 - 2)) + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{((34 \times 5) - 10)}{(8 \times (9 + ((7^2) - 6)))} := \frac{((34 + 5) \times 10)}{((8 \times (9 \times (7 \times 2))) + 6)} := \frac{((34 - 5) \times 10)}{((8 \times (97 - 2)) - 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times ((4 + 5) \times 10))}{(((8 + 9) \times 7) - 2) \times 6} := \frac{(3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (1 - 0))))}{((8 + (9 + (7 + 2))) \times 6)} := \frac{(3 \times (4 + (5 + (1 - 0))))}{((8 - (9 - (7 \times 2))) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(34 \times (5 + 10))}{((8 + 9) \times (72 + 6))} := \frac{(345 + 10)}{(897 + 26)} := \frac{(345 - 10)}{(897 - 26)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{36780}{51492} &:= \frac{(((3 \times 6) - 7) \times 80)}{(((5 \times (1 \times 4) - 9) \times 2)} := \frac{(((3 + 6) \times 7) - (8 - 0))}{(5 + (1 \times (4 \times (9 \times 2))))} := \frac{((3 \times (6 - 7)) + (8 - 0))}{(5 - (1 + (4 - (9 - 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times 6) + (7 + 80))}{(51 + (4 + 92))} := \frac{((3 + (6 + 7)) \times 80)}{(((5 - 1)^4) \times (9 - 2))} := \frac{((3 + 67) \times (8 - 0))}{((5 + (14 + 9))^2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (6 - (78 - 0)))}{(5 + ((1 + 49) \times 2))} := \frac{(3 - (6 + (7 - 80)))}{(5 + ((1^4) + 92))} := \frac{(3 \times (6 + (7 - (8 - 0))))}{(5 + (1 + (4 + (9 + 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + ((6 \times 7) + 80))}{(5 + (1 + ((4 + 9)^2)))} := \frac{(3 + (6 - (7 - (8 - 0))))}{(5 - (1 + ((4 - 9) \times 2)))} := \frac{(3 + (6 \times (7 + 80)))}{(5 \times (149 - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (6 + (7 \times (8 - 0))))}{(5 + (1 + (4 + (9^2))))} := \frac{(36 + (7 - (8 - 0)))}{(5 + (1 \times (4 \times (9 + 2))))} := \frac{(367 + (8 - 0))}{(514 + (9 + 2))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{36918}{52740} &:= \frac{((3 - (6 - (9 + 1))) \times 8)}{(52 + (7 \times (4 - 0)))} := \frac{((3 - (6 + 9)) \times (1 - 8))}{(((5 \times 2) - 7) \times 40)} := \frac{((3 \times (69 - 1)) - 8)}{(5 \times (2 \times (7 \times (4 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times 69) - 18)}{(5 \times ((2 \times 7) + 40))} := \frac{((36 \times (9 - 1)) - 8)}{((5 - (2 - 7)) \times 40)} := \frac{((3 - 69) \times (1 - 8))}{(5 \times ((2^7) + (4 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - ((6 - (9 + 1)) \times 8))}{(5 - (2 - (7 + 40)))} := \frac{(3 - (6 - ((9 + 1) \times 8)))}{(5 \times (2 \times (7 + (4 - 0))))} := \frac{(3 - (6 - (9 + (1^8))))}{(5 + (2 + (7 - (4 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (6 + (9 - (1 \times 8))))}{(5 \times (2 \times (7 - (4 - 0))))} := \frac{(3 \times (6 + (9 \times 18)))}{(((5^2) - 7) \times 40)} := \frac{(3 + (6 \times (9 + (1 \times 8))))}{(5 \times (2 + (7 \times (4 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (6 \times (9 + (1^8))))}{(5 \times ((2 \times 7) + (4 - 0)))} := \frac{(36 - (9 - (1^8)))}{(5 + (2 - (7 - 40)))} := \frac{(369 + (1 + 8))}{(5 \times (27 \times (4 - 0)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{43980}{61572} &:= \frac{(((4 \times 3) - 9) \times 80)}{(6 \times (1 + (57 - 2)))} := \frac{((4 \times (3 + 9)) - (8 - 0))}{((6 + (15 + 7)) \times 2)} := \frac{((4 \times 3) + 9)}{((6 + (1 \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (3 - (9 + 80)))}{((6 + (1 \times 57)) \times 2)} := \frac{((4^3) - (9 - 80))}{((6 + 15) \times (7 + 2))} := \frac{((4 + 3) \times (9 \times 80))}{(((6 + (1 + 5)) \times 7)^2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (3 \times 9) + 9)}{(6 + (15 - 72))} := \frac{(4 \times ((3 \times 9) + 9))}{(6 + (15 - 72))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (3 \times (9 + (8 - 0))))}{(6 \times (1 \times (5 \times (7 \times 2))))} := \frac{(4 + ((3 + 9) \times (8 - 0)))}{((6 - (1 - 5)) \times (7 \times 2))} := \frac{(4 + (3 \times (9 + 8))}{(6 + (1 + (5 \times (7 \times 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (39 - (8 - 0)))}{(6 - (1 + (5 - (7^2))))} := \frac{(43 + (9 \times (8 - 0)))}{(6 + (157 - 2))} := \frac{(43 + (9 + (8 - 0)))}{(6 + (1 + (5 + 7^2)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{51624}{70983} &:= \frac{(((5 \times (1 \times 6)) + 2) \times 4)}{((7 - (0 - 9)) \times (8 + 3))} := \frac{(((5 + (1 + 6))^2) \times 4)}{(709 + 83)} := \frac{((5 - (1 - (6 + 2))) \times 4)}{(70 - (9 - (8 - 3)))} \\ &:= \frac{((5 \times 16) + (2 \times 4))}{(70 + ((9 + 8) \times 3))} := \frac{((5 + (1 + (6^2))) \times 4)}{(7 \times (0 + (9 + (8 \times 3))))} := \frac{((5 + (1 + (6 + 2))) \times 4)}{(7 \times ((0 \times 9) + (8 + 3)))} \\ &:= \frac{((5 + 16) \times 24)}{(7 \times (0 + (9 \times (8 + 3))))} := \frac{((5 - 1) \times (6 \times (2^4)))}{(7 - (0 - (9 + (8^3))))} := \frac{((51 \times (6 - 2)) + 4)}{(70 + (9 \times (8 \times 3)))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 - (1 - (6 + (2 - 4))))}{(7 - (0 - (9 - (8 - 3))))} := \frac{(5 \times (1 \times (6 - (2 - 4))))}{(70 + (9 - (8 \times 3)))} := \frac{(5 \times (1 \times (6 \times 24)))}{(7 - (0 - 983))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 \times (16 + (2 \times 4)))}{(((7 \times (0 + 9)) - 8) \times 3)} := \frac{(5 + (1 - (6 - (2^4))))}{(7 + (0 - (9 - (8 \times 3))))} := \frac{(5 + (1 + (62 + 4)))}{(7 - (0 - (9 + 83)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{71456}{89320} &:= \frac{(((7 - (1 - 4)) \times 5) - 6)}{(8 + ((9 \times 3) + 20))} := \frac{((7 - (1 - 4)) \times 56)}{((8 + (9 \times 3)) \times 20)} := \frac{((7 \times (1 + (4 + 5))) + 6)}{(89 + (3 \times (2 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{((7 \times (1 + (4 + 5))) - 6)}{(8 \times (9 + (3 - (2 - 0))))} := \frac{((7 + ((1^4) \times 5)) \times 6)}{(89 + (3 - (2 - 0)))} := \frac{((7 + (1 \times (4 + 5))) \times 6)}{(8 \times (9 + (3 \times (2 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{((7 + (1 - 4)) \times (5 \times 6))}{((8 \times 9) + 3) \times (2 - 0)} := \frac{((7 + (1 - 4)) \times 56)}{((8 + (9 - 3)) \times 20)} := \frac{(7 - (((1 - 4) \times 5) + 6))}{(8 + ((9 - 3) \times (2 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 - (1 - (4 + (5 \times 6))))}{((8 \times (9 - 3)) + (2 - 0))} := \frac{(7 - (1 \times (4 + (5 - 6))))}{(8 - (9 - (3 \times (2 - 0))))} := \frac{(7 - (1 + (4 - (5 \times 6))))}{(8 + (9 + (3 + 20)))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 \times (1 - (4 - (5 + 6))))}{((8 + (9 \times 3)) \times (2 - 0))} := \frac{(7 + (1 \times (4 - (5 - 6))))}{(8 + ((9 \times 3) - 20))} := \frac{(7 + (1 + (4 + 56)))}{((8 + 9) \times (3 + (2 - 0)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{71536}{89420} &:= \frac{(((7 + 1) \times 5) + 36)}{(89 + (4 + (2 - 0)))} := \frac{(((7 - (1 + (5 - 3))) \times 6)}{(8 \times 9) - (42 - 0))} := \frac{((7 + 1) \times (5 - (3 - 6)))}{(8 + (9 \times (4 \times (2 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{((71 \times (5 - 3)) - 6)}{((89 - 4) \times (2 - 0))} := \frac{(7 - (1 - (5 \times (3 \times 6))))}{(8 \times (9 + (4 + (2 - 0))))} := \frac{(7 - (1 - (5 + (3 + 6))))}{(8 + (9 + (4 \times (2 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 - (9 - (4 + (2 - 0))))}{(7 - (1 + (5 + (3 - 6))))} := \frac{(7 \times (1 \times ((5 - 3) \times 6)))}{(7 \times (1 \times (5 - (3 - 6))))} := \frac{(7 \times (1 \times (5 - (3 - 6))))}{(7 \times (1 \times (5 - (3 - 6))))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 - (9 - (4 + (2 - 0))))}{(7 \times (1 + (53 - 6)))} := \frac{(89 - (4 - 20))}{(7 + (1 - (5 - (3 + 6))))} := \frac{(((8 + 9) \times 4) + (2 - 0))}{(7 + (1 \times (5 \times (3 + 6))))} \\ &:= \frac{((8 + (9 + 4)) \times 20)}{(7 + (1 \times (5 + 36)))} := \frac{(8 - (9 + (4 - 20)))}{(7 + (1 + (5 - (3 - 6))))} := \frac{(89 - (4 + 20))}{(71 + ((5 \times 3) - 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 - (9 - 4)) \times 20}{((8 - (9 - 4)) - 20)} := \frac{(8 \times (9 - 4)) - 20}{(8 + (94 - (2 - 0)))} \end{aligned}$$

• **Four Digit's Numerator**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1953}{468720} &:= \frac{(((1^9) + 5)^3)}{((4 + 68) \times 720)} := \frac{(((1^{95}) \times 3)}{(4 \times (6 + (87 \times (2 - 0))))} := \frac{(((1^{95}) + 3)}{(4 \times (6 \times (8 \times (7 - (2 - 0))))))} \\ &:= \frac{(((1^9) + (5 + 3))}{((4 + 6) \times (8 \times (7 + 20)))} := \frac{(((1^9) + 53)}{((4 + (6 + 8)) \times 720)} := \frac{(1 \times ((9 \times 5) + 3))}{(((4 \times 6) - 8) \times 720)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times ((9 + 5) \times 3))}{((4 + 68) \times (7 \times 20))} := \frac{(1 \times (9 - (5 - 3)))}{(4 \times ((6 + (8 + 7)) \times 20))} := \frac{(1 \times (9 \times (5 - 3)))}{((4 - (6 - 8)) \times 720)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (9 + (5 \times 3)))}{((4 + 6) \times (8 \times (72 - 0)))} := \frac{1^{953}}{(4 \times (6 + ((8 \times 7) - (2 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 + (9 - (5 + 3)))}{(4 \times (6 \times ((8 - 7) \times 20)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (9 - (5 - 3)))}{(4 \times (6 \times (8 + (72 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 + (9 + (5 \times 3)))}{(4 \times ((68 + 7) \times 20))} := \frac{(1 + (9 + (5^3)))}{(4 \times ((6 \times (8 + 7))^2 + 0))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{2615}{397480} & := \frac{((2 \times (6-1)) - 5)}{(3 + (9 + (748 - 0)))} & := \frac{((2 \times 6) - (1 + 5))}{((3 + (9 + 7)) \times (48 - 0))} & := \frac{((2 \times 61) + 5)}{((3 + (9 + (7^4))) \times (8 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{((2 + (6 \times 1)) \times 5)}{((3 + (9 + 7)) \times (4 \times 80))} & := \frac{((2 - 6) \times (1 - 5))}{(39 + ((7^4) - (8 - 0)))} & := \frac{(2 - (6 - (1 \times 5)))}{((3 + ((9 - 7)^4)) \times (8 - 0))} \\ & := \frac{(2 - (6 - (1 + 5)))}{(((3 \times 9) + (7 + 4)) \times (8 - 0))} & := \frac{(2 \times (6 - (1^5)))}{((3 + ((9 - 7)^4)) \times 80)} & := \frac{(2 \times (6 - (1 - 5)))}{(((3 \times 9) + (7 + 4)) \times 80)} \\ & := \frac{(2 \times (6 \times (1 \times 5)))}{((3 + (9 + 7)) \times 480)} & := \frac{(2^{6+1-5})}{((3 + (9 + 7)) \times (4 \times (8 - 0)))} & := \frac{(2 + (6 \times (1^5)))}{(((3 \times (9 - 7))^4) - 80)} \\ & := \frac{(26 - (1 \times 5))}{((3 - 9) \times (7 \times (4 - 80)))} & := \frac{(26 - (1 - 5))}{((3 - (9 \times 7)) \times (4 - 80))} & := \frac{(26 \times (1 \times 5))}{((3^9) - (7 - (4 + 80)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{5976}{203184} & := \frac{(((5 + 9) \times 7) - 6)}{((20 - 3) \times 184)} & := \frac{((5 - (9 - 7)) \times 6)}{((20 + 31) \times (8 + 4))} & := \frac{((5 \times (9 - 7)) + 6)}{((20 \times (3 \times (1 + 8))) + 4)} \\ & := \frac{((5 \times (9 - 7)) - 6)}{((2 - (0 - ((3 + 1) \times 8))) \times 4)} & := \frac{((5 \times 9) - (7 \times 6))}{(20 - (3 - (1 + 84)))} & := \frac{((5 \times 9) + 76)}{(20 - (3 - (1 + (8^4))))} \\ & := \frac{((5^{9-7}) \times 6)}{(20 \times (3 \times (1 + 84)))} & := \frac{((5 + (9 + 7)) \times 6)}{((20 + 31) \times 84)} & := \frac{((5 + (9 - 7)) \times 6)}{((20 - (3 \times 1)) \times 84)} \\ & := \frac{(5 - (9 - (7 \times 6)))}{(20 + (318 \times 4))} & := \frac{(5 - (9 - 76))}{(((20 \times 31) - 8) \times 4)} & := \frac{(5 \times (9 + (7 + 6)))}{(20 \times (3 + 184))} \\ & := \frac{(5 + (9 - (7 + 6)))}{(2 \times (0 + (3 + (18 - 4))))} & := \frac{(5 + (9 \times (7 - 6)))}{((20 \times (3 \times (1 \times 8))) - 4)} & := \frac{(5 + (9 + (7 - 6)))}{(2 \times (0 + (3 \times (1 + 84))))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{6453}{210798} & := \frac{(((6 - (4 - 5)) \times 3)}{(2 - (1 - 0)) \times (7 \times 98))} & := \frac{((6 \times (4 + 5)) + 3)}{(2 + (10 + 7)) \times 98)} & := \frac{((6 \times 4) + (5 \times 3))}{(((2 \times 10) - 7) \times 98)} \\ & := \frac{(((6 + (4 + 5)) \times 3)}{(210 \times (7 \times (9 - 8)))} & := \frac{(((6 + (4 - 5)) \times 3)}{(2 + (10 - 7)) \times 98)} & := \frac{(((6 - 4) \times (5 \times 3))}{((2 + (1 - (0 - 7))) \times 98)} \\ & := \frac{(6 - ((4 - 5) \times 3))}{((2 + (10^7)) \times 98)} & := \frac{(6 \times ((4 \times 5) - 3))}{(2 \times ((10 + 7) \times 98))} & := \frac{(6 \times (4 \times (5 - 3)))}{(2 \times ((1 - (0 - 7)) \times 98))} \\ & := \frac{(6 \times (45 - 3))}{((2 + 10) \times (7 \times 98))} & := \frac{(6^{4-5+3})}{((210 - (7 \times 9)) \times 8)} & := \frac{(6 + ((4 - 5) \times 3))}{(((2 + (1 - (0 - 7))) \times 9) + 8)} \\ & := \frac{(6 + (4 + (5 + 3)))}{(2 \times ((10 - 7) \times 98))} & := \frac{(6 + (4 + 53))}{((2 + (1 - 0)) \times (7 \times 98))} & := \frac{(645 - 3)}{(2 \times (107 \times 98))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9071}{235846} & := \frac{(9 - ((0 \times 7) - 1))}{(2 + (((3 \times (5 + 8)) + 4) \times 6))} & := \frac{(9 - (0 - (7 \times 1)))}{(2 - (3 \times ((5 - 8) \times 46)))} & := \frac{(9 - (0 - (7 + 1)))}{((2 + (3 \times 5)) \times ((8 \times 4) - 6))} \\ & := \frac{(9 - (0 - (7 - 1)))}{((2 + (3 + (5 \times (8 + 4)))) \times 6)} & := \frac{(9 - (0 \times 71))}{(2 \times ((3 \times (5 + (8 \times 4))) + 6))} & := \frac{(9 \times (0 + (7 + 1)))}{(2 \times (3 \times ((5 + 8) \times (4 \times 6))))} \\ & := \frac{(9 \times (0 + (7 - 1)))}{(2 \times ((3 \times (58 \times 4)) + 6))} & := \frac{(9 + ((0 \times 7) - 1))}{((2 \times (3 + 5)) + (8 \times (4 \times 6)))} & := \frac{(9 + (0 - (7 \times 1)))}{(2 \times (3 + (5 + (8 + (4 + 6))))} \\ & := \frac{(9 + (0 - (7 + 1)))}{(2 + (3 + (5 - (8 \times (4 - 6))))} & := \frac{(9 + (0 - (7 - 1)))}{(2 + (3 - (5 - (84 - 6))))} & := \frac{(90 - (7 - 1))}{((2 + (358 + 4)) \times 6)} \\ & := \frac{(90 + (7 \times 1))}{(2 + (35 \times ((8 + 4) \times 6)))} & := \frac{(90 + (7 - 1))}{((2^3) \times ((5 + 8) \times (4 \times 6)))} & := \frac{(90 - 71)}{(2 + ((3 - (5 - 84)) \times 6))} \end{aligned}$$

3.15 16 Equivalent Blocks

- Five Digit's Numerator

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10356}{28479} &:= \frac{(((1^{03}) + 5) \times 6)}{(2 + ((8 \times (4 + 7)) + 9))} := \frac{((1 - (0 - (3 \times 5))) \times 6)}{((2^8) - (4 \times (7 - 9)))} := \frac{((1 - (0 - 3)) \times (5 + 6))}{(((2^{8-4}) \times 7) + 9)} := \frac{((1^{03}) \times 56)}{(2 + (8 \times ((4 \times 7) - 9)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((10 - (3 - 5)) \times 6)}{(2 \times ((8 - (4 - 7)) \times 9))} := \frac{((10 \times (3 \times 5)) - 6)}{(((2 \times 8) + (4 \times 7)) \times 9)} := \frac{((10 + (3 + 5)) \times 6)}{(((2 + 8) \times 4) - 7) \times 9)} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (3 + 56)))}{(2 + (84 + 79))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 - ((3 - 5) \times 6)))}{(((2 + (8 - 4)) \times 7) - 9)} := \frac{(1 \times (0 - (3 - (5 + 6))))}{(2 + (8 - (4 - (7 + 9))))} := \frac{(1 + (0 - (3 - (5 \times 6))))}{(2 - (8 - (4 + 79)))} := \frac{(10 \times (3 - (5 - 6)))}{((28 \times 4) + (7 - 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 \times (3 + (5 - 6)))}{(28 - ((4 - 7) \times 9))} := \frac{(10^{3+5-6})}{((2^8) + ((4 \times 7) - 9))} := \frac{(10 + (3 + (5 + 6)))}{(2 + (8^{4+7-9}))} := \frac{(103 - (5 - 6))}{(284 - (7 - 9))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12069}{37548} &:= \frac{(((1 + (2 - 0))^6) - 9)}{(3^7) + (5 + 48))} := \frac{((1^2 + 0) \times (6 \times 9))}{(3 \times (7 \times ((5 - 4) \times 8)))} := \frac{((1 + (2 - (0 \times 6))) \times 9)}{(3 \times (7 + 5)) + 48)} := \frac{((1 + (2 - (0 \times 6)))^9)}{((3^7) \times ((5 \times 4) + 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (2 - (0 - 6))) \times 9)}{(3 \times (7 \times ((5 \times 4) - 8)))} := \frac{((1 + (2 - 0)) \times (6 \times 9))}{((37 + 5) \times (4 + 8))} := \frac{(1 \times ((20 + 6) \times 9))}{((37 + 54) \times 8)} := \frac{(1 \times (2 \times (0 + (6 \times 9))))}{((3 + ((7 \times 5) + 4)) \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (20 \times (6 \times 9)))}{(3 \times (7 \times (5 \times (4 \times 8))))} := \frac{(1 + (2 - (0 - (6 + 9))))}{(3 - (7 - (5 \times (4 + 8))))} := \frac{(1 + (2 - (0 - 69)))}{((37 - (5 + 4)) \times 8)} := \frac{(1 + (2^{-06+9}))}{(((3^7-5) \times 4) - 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (20 + (6 + 9)))}{(((3 \times 7) + 5) \times 4) + 8)} := \frac{(1 + (20 + 69))}{((3 + 7) \times ((5 \times 4) + 8))} := \frac{(12 \times (0 + (6 \times 9)))}{((37 + 5) \times 48)} := \frac{(120 + 69)}{(3 \times (7 \times ((5 \times 4) + 8)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12984}{35706} &:= \frac{(((1 - (2 - 9)) \times 8) - 4)}{(3 \times (57 - 0)) - 6)} := \frac{(((12 - 9) \times 8) + 4)}{(35 - (7 \times (0 - 6)))} := \frac{((1 + (2 + (9 - 8)))^4)}{(3 - (5 - 706))} := \frac{((1 + (2 + 9)) \times (8 \times 4))}{((3 \times (5 \times 70)) + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (2 + 9)) \times (8 - 4))}{(((3 \times 5) + (7 - 0)) \times 6)} := \frac{((1 + (29 - 8)) \times 4)}{((3^5) - (7 + (0 - 6)))} := \frac{((12 - 9) \times (8 + 4))}{(((3 \times 5 \times (7 - 0))) - 6)} := \frac{(1 - (2 - (9 - (8 - 4))))}{(3 - (5 - (7 - (0 - 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((2 + 9) \times (8 + 4)))}{(357 - (0 - 6))} := \frac{(1 \times ((29 - 8) \times 4))}{((3 \times (5 + 70)) + 6)} := \frac{(1 \times (2 \times ((9 \times 8) + 4)))}{(3 - (5 - (70 \times 6)))} := \frac{(1 \times (29 \times (8 - 4)))}{((3^5) + (70 + 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (2 + (9 - (8 - 4))))}{(35 - (7 - (0 - 6)))} := \frac{(1 + (2 + (9 + (8 + 4))))}{(3 + (57 - (0 - 6)))} := \frac{(1 + (2 + (9 + (8 - 4))))}{(3 + ((5 \times (7 - 0)) + 6))} := \frac{(12 \times (9 \times (8 + 4)))}{(3570 - 6)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13965}{78204} &:= \frac{(((1 + 3)^{9-6}) \times 5)}{(7 \times ((8^2 + 0) \times 4))} := \frac{((1^3) \times (9 + (6 + 5)))}{(7 \times (8 - (2 \times (0 - 4))))} := \frac{((1^3) + (9 + 65))}{(7 \times ((8^2 + 0) - 4))} := \frac{((1 + ((3 \times 9) - 6)) \times 5)}{(7 \times (8 + (20 \times 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (3 \times (9 - 6))) \times 5)}{(7 \times ((8 + (2 - 0)) \times 4))} := \frac{((1 + (3^{9-6})) \times 5)}{(7 \times ((8 + 20) \times 4))} := \frac{((13 + (9 - 6)) \times 5)}{(7 \times (8 \times (2 \times (0 + 4))))} := \frac{(1 \times ((3 \times (9 + 6)) - 5))}{(7 \times (8 + (20 + 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (3 \times (9 + (6 - 5))))}{(7 \times (8 + (2^{04})))} := \frac{(1 + ((3 \times (9 - 6)) + 5))}{(7 \times ((8 \times (2 - 0)) - 4))} := \frac{(1 + ((39 \times 6) + 5))}{(7 \times (8 \times (20 + 4)))} := \frac{(1 + (3 - (9 - 65)))}{(7 \times (8 \times (2 - (0 - 4))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (3 \times (9 - (6 - 5))))}{((7 + (8 + 20)) \times 4)} := \frac{(1 + (39 - (6 \times 5)))}{(7 \times (8 - (2 \times (0 \times 4))))} := \frac{(1 + (39 + (6 \times 5)))}{((78 + 20) \times 4)} := \frac{(13 \times ((9 - 6) \times 5))}{(7 \times ((8 \times 20) - 4))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17052}{46893} &:= \frac{(((1^7 + 0) + 5) \times 2)}{(4 - (6 - (8 + (9 \times 3))))} := \frac{(((1^7 + 0) + 5)^2)}{(4 - (6 - (8 + 93)))} := \frac{(((1 - 7) \times (0 - 5)) - 2)}{(((4 - 6) \times 8) + 93)} := \frac{((1 - (7 \times (0 - 5))) \times 2)}{((4 \times (6 \times 8)) + (9 - 3))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (7 - (0 \times 5))) \times 2)}{((4 \times (6 + 8)) - (9 + 3))} := \frac{((1 + (70 + 5)) \times 2)}{(4 + (6 \times ((8 \times 9) - 3)))} := \frac{((17 - (0 - 5)) \times 2)}{(4 + (((6 \times 8) - 9) \times 3))} := \frac{((17 - (0 - 5))^2)}{((4 + (6 - (8 - 9)))^3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((7 - (0 - 5)) \times 2))}{(4 + (68 - (9 - 3)))} := \frac{(1 \times ((7 - (0 - 5))^2))}{(4 \times ((6 \times (8 + 9)) - 3))} := \frac{(1 \times (7 - (0 - (5^2))))}{(4 + (6 \times (8 + (9 - 3))))} := \frac{(1 \times (7 \times (0 + 52)))}{((4 \times 68) + (9^3))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (7 + (0 - (5 - 2))))}{(46 - (8 + (9 \times 3)))} := \frac{(1 + (7 - (0 \times 52)))}{(4 - (6 \times ((8 - 9) \times 3)))} := \frac{(1 + (7 - (0 - 52)))}{(4 + (68 + 93))} := \frac{(170 + (5 \times 2))}{(468 + (9 \times 3))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{17298}{60543} & := \frac{(((1+(7-2))\times 9)+8)}{(((60-5)\times 4)-3)} := \frac{(((1-7)\times 2)+(9\times 8))}{(6\times(0+(5\times(4+3))))} := \frac{(((17^2)-9)\times 8)}{((6^5)+(4^3))} := \frac{((17^2)\times 98)}{((6-(0-(5-4)))^3)} \\ & := \frac{((17^2)+(9-8))}{(6-(0-((5-4)^3)))} := \frac{(1-(7-((2\times 9)+8)))}{(6-((0\times 5)-(4^3)))} := \frac{(1-(7-(2\times(9+8))))}{(60-(5-43))} := \frac{(1\times((7^2)-(9-8)))}{(6-(0-(54\times 3)))} \\ & := \frac{(1\times(7\times(2\times(9-8))))}{(1+(7\times(2+9))+8)} := \frac{(1+(7\times(2+9))+8)}{(1+(7\times 2)+(9-8))} := \frac{(1+(7-(2\times(9-8))))}{(1+(7-(2\times(9-8))))} \\ & := \frac{(6-((0\times 5)-43))}{(1+(7-(2-98)))} := \frac{((60\times 5)+(4-3))}{(1+(7\times(2+9-8)))} := \frac{(60-(5-(4-3)))}{(1+(7+((2\times 9)+8)))} := \frac{((6-(0-(5-4))\times 3)}{(1+(7+((2\times 9)-8)))} \\ & := \frac{(1+(7-(2-98)))}{((60\times 5)+(4^3))} := \frac{(1+(7\times(2+9-8)))}{((6-(0-5))\times(4+3))} := \frac{(1+(7+((2\times 9)+8)))}{(60-(5-(4^3)))} := \frac{(1+(7+((2\times 9)-8)))}{(6-(0-(54+3)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{18697}{53420} & := \frac{((1-(8-(6+9)))\times 7)}{(5\times(34-(2-0)))} := \frac{((1^{86})\times(9\times 7))}{(5\times(34+(2-0)))} := \frac{((1+((8-6)\times 9))\times 7)}{(((5\times 3)+4)\times 20)} := \frac{((1+(8\times(6+9)))\times 7)}{(((5^3)-4)\times 20)} \\ & := \frac{((1+(8+(6+9)))\times 7)}{(((5^3)\times 4)-20)} := \frac{((1+(8+(6-9)))\times 7)}{(5\times(3\times(4\times(2-0))))} := \frac{(1-(8+((6-9)\times 7)))}{((5\times(3\times 4))-20)} := \frac{(1-(8+(6-97)))}{(5\times(3\times(4^2+0)))} \\ & := \frac{(1\times(((8\times 6)+9)\times 7))}{((53+4)\times 20)} := \frac{(1\times(((8\times 6)-9)\times 7))}{((5+34)\times 20)} := \frac{(1\times(((8+6)\times 9)-7))}{(5\times(34\times(2-0)))} := \frac{(1\times((8+6)\times(9+7)))}{((5+3)\times(4\times 20))} \\ & := \frac{(1\times((8+6)\times(9-7)))}{((5+(3-4)\times 20)} := \frac{(1\times((8-6)\times(9\times 7)))}{(5\times(3\times(4+20)))} := \frac{(1\times(8+(6+(9\times 7))))}{(((5\times 3)-4)\times 20)} := \frac{(1+(8+(6+97)))}{(((5-3)^4)\times 20)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{19602}{45738} & := \frac{((1^9)\times(6\times(0+2)))}{(4\times(5+(7+(3-8))))} := \frac{((1^9)\times(60\times 2))}{(4\times(5+(73-8)))} := \frac{(1\times(9-(6-(0\times 2))))}{(4+(5-(7+(3-8))))} := \frac{(1\times(9-(6\times(0\times 2))))}{(4+(5+(7-(3-8))))} \\ & := \frac{(1\times(9-(6\times(0-2))))}{(1\times(9-(6\times(0\times 2))))} := \frac{(1\times(9\times(6-(0\times 2))))}{(1\times(9\times(6\times(0+2))))} := \frac{(1\times(9\times(6-(0-2))))}{(1\times(9\times(6\times(0+2))))} \\ & := \frac{(45-(7-(3+8)))}{(1\times(9+(6-(0\times 2))))} := \frac{(45+(73+8))}{(1\times(96-(0\times 2)))} := \frac{(4\times((5\times(7+3))-8))}{(1+(9-(6+(0-2))))} := \frac{((4\times 57)+(3\times 8))}{(1+(9+602))} \\ & := \frac{(1\times(9+(6-(0\times 2))))}{((4-5)\times(7\times(3-8)))} := \frac{(1\times(96-(0\times 2)))}{((4\times(57-3))+8)} := \frac{(1+(9-(6+(0-2))))}{(4+(5\times(7+(3-8))))} := \frac{(1+(9+602))}{(4\times((5\times 73)-8))} \\ & := \frac{(19\times(6-(0\times 2)))}{((4\times 57)+38)} := \frac{(19\times(60\times 2))}{(4\times(5\times(7\times 38)))} := \frac{(19+(6-(0-2)))}{(4+((5\times 7)+(3\times 8)))} := \frac{(196-(0-2))}{(457-(3-8))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{21948}{60357} & := \frac{((2-(1-(9+4)))\times 8)}{(((60+3)\times 5)-7)} := \frac{((2-(1-9))\times 48)}{(60\times((3\times 5)+7))} := \frac{((2\times(1+(9-4)))+8)}{(((6\times(0+(3+5)))+7)} := \frac{((2+(1\times 9))\times(4+8))}{(6-(0-357))} \\ & := \frac{(2-(1+(9-(4+8))))}{(6-(0-(3-(5-7))))} := \frac{(2\times((19-4)\times 8))}{(603+57)} := \frac{(2\times(1-(9-(4\times 8))))}{(6\times(0+((3\times 5)+7)))} := \frac{(2\times(1\times(94-8)))}{((60\times(3+5))-7)} \\ & := \frac{(2\times(1+(9-(4-8))))}{((6-((0\times 3)-5))\times 7)} := \frac{(2\times(1+(9+(4\times 8))))}{(60+(3\times 57))} := \frac{(2\times(1\times(9+(4-8))))}{(60+(35-7))} := \frac{(2+(1\times(94-8)))}{(6-(0-((3^5)-7)))} \\ & := \frac{(2+(1+(9-(4-8))))}{(6-(0-(3+(5\times 7))))} := \frac{(2+(1+(9+(4+8))))}{(6-(0-(3+57)))} := \frac{(2+(1+(9+(4-8))))}{(((6+(0-3))\times 5)+7)} := \frac{(2+(1+(9+48)))}{(60+(3\times(5\times 7)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{34608}{95172} & := \frac{(((3\times 4)+(6-0))\times 8)}{(9\times((5+17)\times 2))} := \frac{((3-(4-(6-0)))\times 8)}{((9\times(5+(1\times 7)))+2)} := \frac{((3\times(4\times(6-0)))+8)}{(((9\times 5)-1)\times(7-2))} := \frac{((3\times(4\times(6-0)))-8)}{(9-(5-172))} \\ & := \frac{((3+(4-(6-0)))\times 8)}{(9+(5-(1-(7+2))))} := \frac{((34-(6-0))\times 8)}{(((9\times 5)-1)\times(7\times 2))} := \frac{((3-46)\times(0-8))}{(951-(7-2))} := \frac{(3\times((4\times(6-0))+8))}{(9+(51\times(7-2)))} \\ & := \frac{(3\times((4\times(6-0))-8))}{(9+(51+72))} := \frac{(3\times((4+(6-0))\times 8))}{(((95-1)\times 7)+2)} := \frac{(3\times(4-(6\times(0\times 8))))}{(9+(5+(17+2)))} := \frac{(3\times(4\times(6-(0\times 8))))}{(9\times((5-(1-7))\times 2))} \\ & := \frac{(34-(6-(0\times 8)))}{(9-(5-(1+72)))} := \frac{(34-(6-(0-8)))}{(9+(51-(7-2)))} := \frac{(34-(6+(0-8)))}{(9\times(5+(1+(7-2))))} := \frac{(34+(6+(0-8)))}{((9+(5\times(1\times 7)))\times 2)} \end{aligned}$$

37512
46890

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{((3 \times 7) + 51) \times 2}{((4 + (6 - 8)) \times 90)} &:= \frac{(((3^{7-5}) - 1)^2)}{(4 - (6 + (8 - 90)))} := \frac{((3 \times ((7 \times 5) - 1)) + 2)}{(4 + ((6 + 8) \times (9 - 0)))} := \frac{((3 \times (7 + (5 \times 1)))^2)}{((4 + (6 + 8)) \times 90)} \\ &:= \frac{((3 + (7 \times 51)) \times 2)}{(4 + (6 + 890))} := \frac{(3 - (7 - (5 \times 12)))}{(4 - (6 - (8 \times (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(3 - (7 \times (5 - 12)))}{((4 \times (6 + 8)) + (9 - 0))} := \frac{(3 \times (((7 \times 5) + 1)^2))}{((46 + 8) \times 90)} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times ((7 + (5 \times 1))^2))}{((4 - (6 - 8)) \times 90)} := \frac{(3 \times ((7 + 5) \times (1 + 2)))}{((4 + 68) \times 90)} := \frac{(3 \times (7 + (5 \times (1^2))))}{(46 + (8 - (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 + (7 - (5 - (1 + 2))))}{(4 - (6 \times (8 - (9 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (7 \times (5 \times (1 + 2))))}{(46 + (89 - 0))} := \frac{(3 + (7 + (5 - (1 + 2))))}{(4 - (6 - (8 + (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(3 + (7 + (5 \times (1 \times 2))))}{((4 \times 6) - (8 - (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 + (7 + (5 + (1^2))))}{(4 \times (6 + (8 - (9 - 0))))} \end{aligned}$$

38160
45792

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{((3 \times (8 \times 1)) + (6 - 0))}{(4 \times (5 - (7 - (9 + 2))))} &:= \frac{((3 \times (8 - 1)) - (6 - 0))}{(4 + ((5 - (7 - 9)) \times 2))} := \frac{((3 \times 8) + (1 + 60))}{((4 \times ((5 \times 7) - 9)) - 2)} := \frac{((3 \times 8) + (16 - 0))}{(4 - (5 - (7 \times (9 - 2))))} \\ &:= \frac{((3 + (8 \times 1)) \times 60)}{((4 + 5) \times (7 + (9^2)))} := \frac{((3 + (8 + 1)) \times 60)}{(4 \times ((5 + 7) \times (9 \times 2)))} := \frac{((3 + (8 - 1)) \times (6 - 0))}{(4 + (57 + (9 + 2)))} := \frac{((3 - 8) \times (1 - (6 - 0)))}{((4 \times (5 - (7 - 9))) + 2)} \\ &:= \frac{(3 - (8 - (1 \times 60)))}{((4^{5+7-9}) + 2)} := \frac{(3 \times (8 + (1 + (6 - 0))))}{(4 + (57 - (9 - 2)))} := \frac{(3 \times (81 - (6 - 0)))}{((4 \times (5 + (7 \times 9))) - 2)} := \frac{(3 + (8 - (1 \times (6 - 0))))}{((4 \times 5) - (7 + (9 - 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (8 - (1^6 + 0)))}{(4 - ((5 \times (7 - 9)) + 2))} := \frac{(3 + (8 - (1 - 60)))}{(4 - (5 + (7 - 92)))} := \frac{(3 + (81 + (6 - 0)))}{(4 + (5 + (7 + 92)))} := \frac{(381 - (6 - 0))}{(457 - (9 - 2))} \end{aligned}$$

39120
54768

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{(((3 \times 9) - 1) \times 20)}{((5 + 47) \times (6 + 8))} &:= \frac{((3 \times (9 \times 1)) - (2 - 0))}{(5 - (4 - ((7 \times 6) - 8)))} := \frac{((3 \times (9 + 1)) + 20)}{(5 + (4 - (7 - 68)))} := \frac{((3 + (9 \times 1)) \times 20)}{((5 - 4) \times (7 \times (6 \times 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{((3 + (9 + 1)) \times 20)}{((54 \times 7) - (6 + 8))} := \frac{((39 + 1) \times (2 - 0))}{((5 - (4 - (7 + 6))) \times 8)} := \frac{(3 - (9 - (1 + 20)))}{((5 - 4) \times (7 + (6 + 8)))} := \frac{(3 \times ((9 + 1) \times (2 - 0)))}{(5 + (4 + (7 + 68)))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times ((9 + 1)^2 + 0))}{(5 \times (4 \times (7 + (6 + 8))))} := \frac{(3 \times (9 \times (1 \times 20)))}{((5 + 4) \times (76 + 8))} := \frac{(3 \times (9 \times 120))}{(54 \times (76 + 8))} := \frac{(3 \times (9 + (1^2 + 0)))}{(5 - (4 + (7 - (6 \times 8))))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (9 + (1 + 20)))}{((5 \times (4 \times 7)) - (6 + 8))} := \frac{(3 + (9 - (1 \times (2 - 0))))}{(5 + (4 + (7 + (6 - 8))))} := \frac{(39 + (1^2 + 0))}{(5 - (4 - (7 + (6 \times 8))))} := \frac{(39 + (1 - 20))}{((5 \times (4 \times (7 - 6))) + 8)} \end{aligned}$$

41265
90783

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{(((4 + 1) \times (2^6)) - 5)}{(9 \times (0 + (7 \times (8 + 3))))} &:= \frac{((4 - (1 - (2 \times 6))) \times 5)}{((9 \times (0 + 7)) - 8) \times 3} := \frac{((4 - (1 - (2 + 6))) \times 5)}{(90 + (7 + (8 \times 3)))} := \frac{((4 \times (1 - (2 - 6))) - 5)}{(9 - ((0 \times 7) - (8 \times 3)))} \\ &:= \frac{((4 + (1 - (2 - 6))) \times 5)}{(9 - (0 - (7 + 83)))} := \frac{((4 + (1 \times (2 \times 6))) \times 5)}{((9 - (0 - 7)) \times (8 + 3))} := \frac{((4 + (1 \times (2 + 6))) \times 5)}{((9 \times (0 + (7 + 8))) - 3)} := \frac{((41^2) - (6 + 5))}{(90 + (7 \times (8^3)))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - (1 - (2 \times (6 + 5))))}{(90 - (7 \times (8 - 3)))} := \frac{(4 \times ((1^{26}) \times 5))}{(9 - (0 - (7 \times (8 - 3))))} := \frac{(4 \times ((12 + 6) \times 5))}{(9 - (0 - 783))} := \frac{(4 \times (1 - (2 - (6 + 5))))}{(90 - (7 - (8 - 3)))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (1 \times (2 \times (6 \times 5))))}{(9 - (0 - (7 + (8^3))))} := \frac{(4 + ((1^{26}) + 5))}{((9 + (0 - 7)) \times (8 + 3))} := \frac{4 + 1^{265}}{(9 - (0 - (7 - (8 - 3))))} := \frac{(4 + (1 + (2 \times (6 \times 5))))}{(90 + ((7 \times 8) - 3))} \end{aligned}$$

45810
73296

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{((4 - (5 - 8)) \times 10)}{(7 \times (3 - (2 - (9 + 6))))} &:= \frac{((4 \times (5 \times 8)) - 10)}{((7 + (3 \times (2 + 9))) \times 6)} := \frac{((4 + (5 - 8)) \times 10)}{(7 + (3 + (2 \times (9 - 6))))} := \frac{((4 + 5) \times (8 \times 10))}{((7 + (3 + 2)) \times 96)} \\ &:= \frac{((45 \times 8) - 10)}{((7 + 3) \times (2 + (9 \times 6)))} := \frac{(4 - (5 - (81 - 0)))}{(4 - (5 - (81 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times ((5 \times 8) + 10))}{(4 \times ((5 \times 8) + 10))} := \frac{((7 - (3 + 2)) \times 96)}{(4 \times ((5 \times 8) - 10))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (5 \times (8 - (1 - 0))))}{(4 \times (5 \times (8 - (1 - 0))))} := \frac{((7 \times 32) - 96)}{(4 \times (5 \times (8 + (1 - 0))))} := \frac{((7 \times 32) + 96)}{(4 \times (5 \times (8 + 10)))} := \frac{((7 - (3 + 2)) \times 96)}{(4 \times (5 \times (81 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{((7 - 3) \times (2 + (9 \times 6)))}{(4 + ((5 \times 8) + (1 - 0)))} := \frac{((7 + (32 + 9)) \times 6)}{(45 \times (8 - (1 - 0)))} := \frac{((7 - (3 - 2)) \times 96)}{(45 \times (8 + (1 - 0)))} := \frac{(((7 \times 3)^2) - 9) \times 6}{(45 + (8 \times 10))} \\ &:= \frac{((73 + (2 - (9 - 6))))}{(7 \times (3 \times ((2 \times 9) + 6)))} := \frac{((7 + (3 + 2)) \times (9 \times 6))}{((7 \times 3 + 2) \times (9 \times 6))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{47130}{65982} &:= \frac{((4 \times (7 + 1)) + (3 - 0))}{(6 + (59 - (8 \times 2)))} := \frac{((4 + (7 + 1)) \times 30)}{(6 \times ((5 + 9) \times (8 - 2)))} := \frac{((4 + (7 - 1)) \times (3 - 0))}{(6 \times (5 + ((9 - 8) \times 2)))} := \frac{(4 \times ((7 + 1) \times 30))}{(6 \times ((5 + 9) \times (8 \times 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (7 + (1 - (3 - 0))))}{(((6 \times (5 \times (9 - 8))) - 2))} := \frac{(4 \times (7 + (13 - 0)))}{(6 + (((5 \times 9) + 8) \times 2))} := \frac{(4 + ((7 - 1)^3 + 0))}{(((6 \times (59 - 8)) + 2))} := \frac{(4 + (7 - (1^3 + 0)))}{(6 + (5 + (9 - (8 - 2))))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - (5 + (9 - (8^2))))}{(4 + (7 - (1 - 30)))} := \frac{(6 - (5 - ((9 + 8) \times 2)))}{(4 + (7 \times (1 \times (3 - 0))))} := \frac{(6 + ((5 \times 9) + 82))}{(4 + (7 \times (13 - 0)))} := \frac{(6 + (5 \times (9 - (8 - 2))))}{(4 + (7 + (1 + (3 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (71 + 30))}{(6 + (59 + 82))} := \frac{(4 + (71 - 30))}{(65 - ((9 - 8) \times 2))} := \frac{(47 + (1 \times (3 - 0)))}{(6 - ((5 - 9) \times (8 \times 2)))} := \frac{(47 + (13 - 0))}{(6 + (5 - (9 - 82)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{50463}{72891} &:= \frac{((5 - (0 - (4 + 6))) \times 3)}{((7^2) + (8 + (9 - 1)))} := \frac{((5 - (0 - (4 - 6))) \times 3)}{(7 + ((2 \times 8) - (9 + 1)))} := \frac{((5 - (0 - 4)) \times (6 + 3))}{((7 - (2 - 8)) \times (9 \times 1))} := \frac{((5 - (0 - 4)) \times 63)}{(728 + 91)} \\ &:= \frac{((5 + (0 - 4)) \times 63)}{((7 + (2 - 8)) \times 91)} := \frac{((50 \times (4 \times 6)) - 3)}{(7 \times ((2^8) - (9 \times 1)))} := \frac{((50 + (4 - 6)) \times 3)}{(((7 + (2 \times 8)) \times 9) + 1)} := \frac{(5 - (0 - (4 + (6 \times 3))))}{(7 + (2 \times (8 + (9 - 1))))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 - (0 - (4 + (6 + 3))))}{(7 + (2 + (8 + (9 \times 1))))} := \frac{(5 - (0 - (4 + 63)))}{(7 - (2 - (8 + 91)))} := \frac{(5 - (0 - (46 + 3)))}{(7 - (2 - ((8 \times 9) + 1)))} := \frac{(5 \times ((0 \times 4) + (6 \times 3)))}{((7 - (2 - 8)) \times (9 + 1))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 \times (0 + (4 \times (6 + 3))))}{((7 \times (28 + 9)) + 1)} := \frac{(50 + (46 + 3))}{(72 + ((8 \times 9) - 1))} := \frac{(504 \times (6 + 3))}{(728 \times (9 \times 1))} := \frac{(504 - 63)}{(7 \times (2 + (89 \times 1)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{51832}{64790} &:= \frac{(((5 - 1) \times (8 \times 3))^2)}{(((6 - 4)^7) \times 90)} := \frac{((5 - (1 - (8 \times 3))) \times 2)}{(6 + (4 \times (7 + (9 - 0))))} := \frac{((5 - (1^8)) \times 32)}{((6 + 4) \times (7 + (9 - 0)))} := \frac{((5 - (1^8))^{3+2})}{(((6^4) - (7 + (9 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{((5 \times (1 + (8 - 3))) + 2)}{((6 \times 4) + (7 + (9 - 0)))} := \frac{((5 \times 18) - (3 \times 2))}{(6 + ((4 + 7) \times (9 - 0)))} := \frac{((5 \times 18) + (3 \times 2))}{(6 \times (4 + (7 + (9 - 0))))} := \frac{((5 + ((1^8) \times 3))^2)}{(64 + (7 + (9 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{((5 + 1)^{8-3-2})}{((6 + (4 - 7)) \times 90)} := \frac{(5 - ((1 - 8) \times (3^2)))}{(6 - (4 + (7 - 90)))} := \frac{(5 - (1 - (8 \times (3 \times 2))))}{(6 - (4 - (7 \times (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(5 \times ((1 + (8 - 3)) \times 2))}{((6 \times (4 + 7)) + (9 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 \times (1 + (8 - (3 + 2))))}{(6 + ((4 \times 7) - (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(5 + (1 \times (8 - (3^2))))}{(((6 - 4) \times 7) - (9 - 0))} := \frac{(51 \times (8 \times (3 \times 2)))}{((6 + (4 \times 7)) \times 90)} := \frac{(518 - (3 \times 2))}{(6 + (4 + (7 \times 90)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{54312}{67890} &:= \frac{(((5 \times 4) + 3) \times 12)}{((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + (9 - 0))} := \frac{(((5^4) \times (3 - 1))^2)}{((6 + (7 - 8))^9 + 0)} := \frac{(((5 \times (4 \times (3 \times 1))))^2)}{(((6 \times 7) + 8) \times 90)} := \frac{(((5 \times (4 + (3 - 1))) + 2)}{(6 - ((7 \times 8) - 90))} \\ &:= \frac{(((5 + (4 + (3 \times 1)))^2)}{((6 \times (7 + 8)) + 90)} := \frac{(((5 - 4) \times 312)}{(6 \times ((7 \times 8) + (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(((54 + (3 - 1)) \times 2)}{((6 \times 7) + (8 + 90))} := \frac{(5 \times (4 - (3 - (1 + 2))))}{(((6 \times 7) - (8 + (9 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 \times (4 \times (3 - (1^2))))}{(67 - (8 + (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(5 \times (4 \times (3 \times (1^2))))}{(6 + (78 - (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(5 \times (4 \times (3 \times (1 + 2))))}{((67 + 8) \times (9 - 0))} := \frac{(5 \times (4 \times (3 + (1 \times 2))))}{(6 + (7 \times (8 + (9 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + ((4^3) - (1^2)))}{(6 + (7 + (8 \times (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(5 + (4 + (3 \times (1^2))))}{(6 - ((7 - 8) \times (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(5 + (4 + (3 \times (1 + 2))))}{((6 + (7 - 8)) \times (9 - 0))} := \frac{(5 + (4 + (3 + 12)))}{(6 + (7 + (8 + (9 - 0))))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{54702}{63819} &:= \frac{((5 - (4 + 7)) \times (0 - 2))}{(6 - (3 + (8 - 19)))} := \frac{((5 \times (4 \times (7 - 0))) - 2)}{(6 + (3 + (8 \times 19)))} := \frac{((5 + 4) \times (70 + 2))}{(((6 - (3 - 81)) \times 9)} := \frac{((5 + 4) \times 702)}{((6 + 3) \times 819)} \\ &:= \frac{((5 - 4) \times (70 + 2))}{(6 \times (3 - (8 - 19)))} := \frac{((5 - 47) \times (0 - 2))}{(((6 \times 3) + (8 \times (1 + 9)))} := \frac{(5 - (4 - (7 + (0 - 2))))}{(6 + (3 + (8 - (1 + 9))))} := \frac{(5 \times ((4 - 7) \times (0 - 2)))}{(6 + (38 - (1 \times 9)))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 \times (4 - (7 \times (0 - 2))))}{(6 + ((3 + (8 \times 1)) \times 9))} := \frac{(5 + ((4 + (7 - 0))^2))}{(((6 \times ((3 \times 8) - 1)) + 9)} := \frac{(5 + (4 + (7 - (0 - 2))))}{(6 - (3 - (8 + (1 + 9))))} := \frac{(5 + (47 - (0 - 2)))}{(((6 \times (3 + (8 + 1))) - 9)} \\ &:= \frac{(54 \times (7 - (0 \times 2)))}{(63 \times (8 - (1^9)))} := \frac{(54 \times (7 - (0 - 2)))}{(63 \times (8 + (1^9)))} := \frac{(54 \times (7 \times (0 + 2)))}{(63 + 819)} := \frac{(54 \times (70 + 2))}{(6 \times ((3 + 81) \times 9))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{60912}{83754} & := \frac{((6 - (0 - (9 + 1))) \times 2)}{(8 + ((3^7 - 5) \times 4))} := \frac{((6 \times (0 + (9 \times 1))) + 2)}{(83 - (7 - (5 - 4)))} := \frac{((6 \times (0 + 91)) - 2)}{(8 + (37 \times (5 \times 4)))} := \frac{((60 \times 9) + 12)}{(8 - (3 - 754))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 - ((0 \times 91) - 2))}{(8 - (3 - (7 - (5 - 4))))} := \frac{(6 - (0 - (9 + (1^2))))}{((8 \times (3 - 7)) + 54)} := \frac{(6 \times (0 + ((9 - 1) \times 2)))}{((8 \times ((3 \times 7) - 5)) + 4)} := \frac{(6 \times (0 + ((9 - 1)^2)))}{(8 \times (3 + (7 \times (5 + 4))))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 \times (0 + (9 - (1^2))))}{(8 - (3 - (7 + 54)))} := \frac{(6 \times (0 + (9 \times 12)))}{(837 + 54)} := \frac{(6 \times (0 + (9 + (1 + 2))))}{(8 + (37 + 54))} := \frac{(6^{-09+12})}{((8 \times 37) + (5 - 4))} \\
 & := \frac{(60 - ((9 + 1) \times 2))}{(((8 - 3) \times 7) + (5 \times 4))} := \frac{(60 \times (9 - (1^2)))}{(((8 - 3) \times 7) + (5^4))} := \frac{(60 + ((9 + 1) \times 2))}{(83 + (7 + (5 \times 4)))} := \frac{(609 - (1^2))}{((8 \times (3 \times (7 \times 5))) - 4)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{61290}{73548} & := \frac{(((6 + 1)^2) - (9 - 0))}{((7 - 3) \times ((5 \times 4) - 8))} := \frac{(((6 - 1) \times 2) + 90)}{((7 - ((3 - 5) \times 4)) \times 8)} := \frac{((6 - (1 \times 2)) \times 90)}{((7 - (3 - 5)) \times 48)} := \frac{((6 - (1^2)) \times (9 - 0))}{(7 + (35 + (4 + 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{((6 + (1 + 2)) \times 90)}{((7 \times (35 \times 4)) - 8)} := \frac{((6 + 1) \times (2 \times 90))}{(7 \times (3 \times ((5 + 4) \times 8)))} := \frac{((6 - 1) \times (2 + (9 - 0)))}{(7 - (3 - (54 + 8)))} := \frac{((6 - 1) \times (2 + 90))}{(7 - (3 - 548))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 - ((1^2)^9 + 0))}{((7 \times (3 - (5 - 4))) - 8)} := \frac{(6 \times ((1^2) + (9 - 0)))}{(7 + (3 + (54 + 8)))} := \frac{(6 \times (1 + (29 - 0)))}{((7 \times ((3 + 5) \times 4)) - 8)} := \frac{(6 + ((1^2) \times (9 - 0)))}{(7 + (3 + ((5 - 4) \times 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 + (1 \times (29 - 0)))}{(7 + ((3 \times (5 + 4)) + 8))} := \frac{(6 + (1 + (2 \times (9 - 0))))}{(7 + (3 - (5 \times (4 - 8))))} := \frac{(61 - (2 + (9 - 0)))}{((7 + (3 - 5)) \times (4 + 8))} := \frac{(61 + (29 - 0))}{((7 - (3 - 5)) \times (4 + 8))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{61470}{98352} & := \frac{((6 - (1 + 4)) \times 70)}{(((9 + 8) \times 3) + 5) \times 2} := \frac{((6 - (1 - 4)) \times 70)}{(983 + (5^2))} := \frac{((6 \times (1 + 4)) + 70)}{(((9 \times 8) + (3 + 5)) \times 2)} := \frac{((6 + (1^4)) \times 70)}{((9 + ((8 \times 3) - 5))^2)} \\
 & := \frac{((6 + 1) \times (4 \times 70))}{(9 + (((8 - 3)^5) + 2))} := \frac{((6 - 1) \times (4 + (7 - 0)))}{((9 \times (8 - (3 - 5))) - 2)} := \frac{((61 + 4) \times (7 - 0))}{((9 + (8 - 3)) \times 52)} := \frac{(6 - ((1^4)^7 + 0))}{(9 + (8 - (3 \times (5 - 2))))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 - ((1^4) - 70))}{(98 - (3 - (5^2)))} := \frac{(6 \times (1 + (4 + 70)))}{(9 \times (8 \times (3 + (5 + 2))))} := \frac{(6 + (1 - (4 - (7 - 0))))}{((9 - 8) \times ((3 + 5) \times 2))} := \frac{(6 + (1 \times (4 + 70)))}{((9 + ((8 + 3) \times 5)) \times 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(6 + (1 + (4 \times (7 - 0))))}{(9 - (8 - (3 + 52)))} := \frac{(6 + (14 + 70))}{(9 + (83 + 52))} := \frac{(61 - (4 + (7 - 0)))}{(((9 \times (8 - 3)) - 5) \times 2)} := \frac{(61 + (4 + 70))}{(9 \times (8 + ((3 + 5) \times 2)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

• **Four Digit's Numerator**

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{1839}{257460} & := \frac{((1^{83}) \times 9)}{((2^5) - (7 + 4)) \times 60} := \frac{((1^8) \times (3 \times 9))}{((2 + (57 + 4)) \times 60)} := \frac{(1 - (8 - (3 + 9)))}{(2 \times (5 \times (7 \times (4 + (6 - 0)))))} := \frac{(1 - (8 - 39))}{(2 \times (5 \times (7 \times (4 + 60))))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times ((8 \times 3) + 9))}{((2 + 5) \times ((7 + 4) \times 60))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 + (3 - 9)))}{(((2^5) \times 7) - (4 - 60))} := \frac{(1^{839})}{(2 \times (5 \times (74 - 60)))} := \frac{(1 + ((8 \times 3) - 9))}{((2^5) \times (7 \times (4 + (6 - 0))))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + ((8 - 3) \times 9))}{((2 + (5 + 7)) \times 460)} := \frac{(1 + (8 - (3 - 9)))}{((2 + (5 + (7 \times 4))) \times 60)} := \frac{(1 + (8 + (3 \times 9)))}{(((2 \times 5) + 74) \times 60)} := \frac{(1 + (8 + (3 - 9)))}{(((2 \times 5) - (7 - 4)) \times 60)} \\
 & := \frac{(18 - (3 + 9))}{((25 - (7 + 4)) \times 60)} := \frac{(18 - (3 - 9))}{((2 + (5 + 7)) \times (4 \times 60))} := \frac{(18 + (3 + 9))}{(25 \times (7 \times (4 \times (6 - 0))))} := \frac{(18 + (3 - 9))}{(2 \times (5 \times (7 \times (4 \times (6 - 0))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{1863}{452709} & := \frac{(((1 + 8)^6) \times 3)}{(4 + 5)^{2+7-0 \times 9}} := \frac{((1^{86}) \times 3)}{((4 + (5 + (2 + 70))) \times 9)} := \frac{((1^{86}) + 3)}{(((4 \times 5) - (2^7)) \times (0 - 9))} := \frac{((1 + (8 + 6)) \times 3)}{(45 \times (27 \times (0 + 9)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (8 - (6 + 3)))}{((45 + (2 + (7 - 0))) \times 9)} := \frac{(1 \times (8 - (6 - 3)))}{(45 \times (27 - (0 \times 9)))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (6 - 3)))}{((4 + 5) \times ((2 + 70) \times 9))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 + (6 + 3)))}{((452 + (7 - 0)) \times 9)} \\
 & := \frac{1^{863}}{((4 - 5) \times (27 \times (0 - 9)))} := \frac{(1 + ((8 - 6)^3))}{((4 + 5) \times (27 \times (0 + 9)))} := \frac{(1 + (8 + (6 \times 3)))}{((4 + 5)^{2-7+09})} := \frac{(1 + (86 + 3))}{((4 + 5) \times (270 \times 9))} \\
 & := \frac{(18 - (6 - 3))}{(45 \times (2 + (70 + 9)))} := \frac{(18 \times (6 \times 3))}{(4 \times (((5 - 2)^7 + 0) \times 9))} := \frac{(18 + (6 \times 3))}{(4 \times ((5 - 2)^{7+0 \times 9}))} := \frac{(18 + (6 - 3))}{(((4 + 5)^2) \times (7 \times (0 + 9)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{8649}{302715} &:= \frac{((8 \times 6) - (4 \times 9))}{(3 \times (0 + ((27 + 1) \times 5)))} := \frac{((8 \times 6) + (4 \times 9))}{((30 - 2) \times (7 \times 15))} := \frac{((8 \times 6) + (4 - 9))}{((30 + 271) \times 5)} := \frac{((8^{6-4}) - 9)}{(((3 \times (0 + (2^7))) + 1) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 - 6) \times (4 \times 9)}{(30 \times (2 \times (7 \times (1 + 5))))} := \frac{(8 - (6 - (4 + 9)))}{((3 - (0 - 2)) \times (7 \times 15))} := \frac{(8 - (6 + (4 - 9)))}{((30 \times (2 + (7 - 1))) + 5)} := \frac{(8 \times ((6 \times 4) - 9))}{(30 \times ((27 + 1) \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8^{6+4-9})}{((30 + (27 - 1)) \times 5)} := \frac{(8 + ((6 \times 4) - 9))}{((30 \times (27 \times 1)) - 5)} := \frac{(8 + (6 - (4 + 9)))}{(3 - (0 - (2 + ((7 - 1) \times 5))))} := \frac{(8 + (6 - (4 - 9)))}{(30 + (((2^7) - 1) \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 + (6 \times 49))}{(302 \times (7 \times (1 \times 5)))} := \frac{(8 + (6 + (4 + 9)))}{((30^2) \times (7 \times 15))} := \frac{(8 + (6 + (4 - 9)))}{((30^2) \times (7 \times (1 \times 5)))} := \frac{(86 - 49)}{((3 - (0 - (2^7+1)))) \times 5} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{8712}{365904} &:= \frac{((8 \times (7 \times 1)) - 2)}{(36 \times (59 - (0 - 4)))} := \frac{(8 - (7 - (1^2)))}{((3 + (6 \times (5 - 9))) \times (0 - 4))} := \frac{(8 - (7 - (1 + 2)))}{((3 - (6 - (5 \times (9 - 0)))) \times 4)} := \frac{(8 - (7 \times (1^2)))}{(3 \times (6 - (5 - (9 - (0 - 4))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 \times (7 - (1^2)))}{(36 \times ((5 + (9 - 0)) \times 4))} := \frac{(8 \times (7 \times (1^2)))}{((3 + (65 \times (9 - 0))) \times 4)} := \frac{(8 + ((7 + 1) \times 2))}{(3 \times (6 \times ((5 + (9 - 0)) \times 4)))} := \frac{(8 + (7 - (1^2)))}{(3 + (65 \times (9 - (0 \times 4))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 + (7 - (1 + 2)))}{((3 + (6 + 5)) \times (9 \times (0 + 4)))} := \frac{(8 + (7 \times (1 + 2)))}{(3 + ((6^5) - (9^{0^4})))} := \frac{(8 + (7 \times (1^2)))}{(36 + (590 + 4))} := \frac{(8 + (7 + (1^2)))}{(3 \times ((65 - (9 - 0)) \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 + (7 + (1 + 2)))}{(((36 \times 5) + (9 - 0)) \times 4)} := \frac{(8 + (7 + 12))}{(3 \times (6 \times (59 - (0 - 4))))} := \frac{(8 + (7 - 12))}{((3 + (6 + 5)) \times (9 - (0 \times 4)))} := \frac{(87 \times (1^2))}{(((3^6) \times 5) + (9 - (0 \times 4)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9238}{157046} &:= \frac{((9 - (2^3)) \times 8)}{(1 - (5 + (70 \times (4 - 6))))} := \frac{((9 - (2^3))^8)}{((1^5) \times (7 - (0 - (4 + 6))))} := \frac{((9^2) + (3 + 8))}{((1 - (5 \times 7)) \times (0 - 46))} := \frac{((9 + (2 \times 3)) \times 8)}{((15 + 70) \times (4 \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 - ((2 \times 3) - 8))}{(1 + (((5 \times (7 - 0)) - 4) \times 6))} := \frac{(9 - ((2 - 3) \times 8))}{(1 + ((5 + (7 - 0)) \times (4 \times 6)))} := \frac{(9 - (2 - (3 + 8)))}{(1 \times (((5 + 70) \times 4) + 6))} := \frac{(9 - (2 - (3 - 8)))}{(1 + ((5 \times (7 - 0)) + (4 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 - (2 \times (3 - 8)))}{(((1^5) - (7 \times (0 - 46)))} := \frac{(9 - (2 + (3 - 8)))}{((1 + (5 - (7 \times (0 - 4)))) \times 6)} := \frac{(9 + ((2 \times 3) - 8))}{(1 \times ((5^7 - 0^4) - 6))} := \frac{(9 + (2 + (3 \times 8)))}{(1 + (570 + (4 \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 + (2 + (3 + 8)))}{(1 \times ((5 \times 70) + (4 \times 6)))} := \frac{(9 + (2 + (3 - 8)))}{((1 + (5 + (7 - (0 - 4)))) \times 6)} := \frac{(9 + (23 - 8))}{((1 + 5) \times (70 + (4 - 6)))} := \frac{(92 - 38)}{((157 + (0 - 4)) \times 6)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9643}{250718} &:= \frac{(((9 - 6) \times 4) - 3)}{((2 \times (50 + 71)) - 8)} := \frac{(9 - ((6 - 4)^3))}{(2 \times (5 - (0 - (7 + (1^8))))} := \frac{(9 - (6 - (4^3)))}{((250 \times (7 \times 1)) - 8)} := \frac{(9 - (6 - (4 - 3)))}{((2 + (5 - (0 - (7 - 1)))) \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 - (6 \times (4 - 3)))}{((2 \times (5 \times (0 + (7 \times 1)))) + 8)} := \frac{(9 - (6 + (4 - 3)))}{((2 \times (5 \times (0 + (7 - 1)))) - 8)} := \frac{(9 + ((6 \times 4) - 3))}{((2 + 50) \times (7 + (1 \times 8)))} := \frac{(9 + ((6 + 4) \times 3))}{(2 \times (507 \times (1^8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 + (6 - (4 + 3)))}{(2 \times ((5 - (0 - (7 + 1))) \times 8))} := \frac{(9 + (6 - (4 - 3)))}{((2 + 50) \times (7 \times (1^8)))} := \frac{(9 + (6 + (4 \times 3)))}{((2 \times (5 \times (0 + 71))) - 8)} := \frac{(9 + (6 + (4 - 3)))}{((2 + 50) \times (7 + (1^8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 + (6 + 43))}{((250 \times (7 - 1)) + 8)} := \frac{(96 - (4^3))}{((2 + 50) \times (7 + (1 + 8)))} := \frac{(96 \times (4 - 3))}{((2 + 50) \times ((7 - 1) \times 8))} := \frac{(96 + (4 \times 3))}{((2 + ((50 \times 7) - 1)) \times 8)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9724}{165308} &:= \frac{((9 - (7 - 2)) \times 4)}{((1 + ((6 + 5) \times (3 - 0))) \times 8)} := \frac{((9 \times 7) - (2^4))}{(1 + (6 \times ((5^3 + 0) + 8)))} := \frac{((9 \times 7) + (2 \times 4))}{(1 + (6 + (5 \times (30 \times 8))))} := \frac{((9 + (7 - 2)) \times 4)}{(1 \times ((6 - (5^3)) \times (0 - 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 - 7) \times (2 + 4)}{(1 + ((65 \times (3 - 0)) + 8))} := \frac{(9 - (7 - (2^4)))}{(1 + (65 + (30 \times 8)))} := \frac{(9 - (7 - (2 + 4)))}{(16 - (5 \times (3 \times (0 - 8))))} := \frac{(9 - (7 + (2 - 4)))}{(1 + (6 + (53 - (0 - 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9^{7-2-4})}{(1 - ((6 + (5 - 30)) \times 8))} := \frac{(9 + ((7 \times 2) - 4))}{(1 + (((6 + 5) \times 30) - 8))} := \frac{(9 + (7 - (2 + 4)))}{(165 - (3 + (0 - 8)))} := \frac{(9 + (7 \times (2 + 4)))}{(((1 + 6) \times (5^3 + 0)) - 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 + (7 + (2 \times 4)))}{((16 + (5 + 30)) \times 8)} := \frac{(9 + (7 + (2^4)))}{(1 \times (6 + (530 + 8)))} := \frac{(9 + (7 + (2 + 4)))}{(1 + (65 + 308))} := \frac{(97 - (2 + 4))}{(1 + (6 + (5 \times 308)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9864}{103572} &:= \frac{(((9 + 8) \times 6) - 4)}{(((1 - (0 - 3))^5) + (7 - 2))} := \frac{(((9 - 8)^6) \times 4)}{(1 + (0 - (3 + (5 - (7^2))))} := \frac{((9 - (8 - 6)) \times 4)}{(((10^3) + 5) \times (7^2))} := \frac{((9 \times (8 - 6)) + 4)}{(1 \times (0 + (3 \times (5 + 72))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 \times (8 - 6)) - 4}{(1 \times (0 + (3 + ((5 + 7^2))))} := \frac{(9 \times 8) - (6 \times 4)}{((1 - (0 - 35)) \times (7 \times 2))} := \frac{((9 \times 8) - (6 - 4))}{(1 \times (0 + (3 \times (5 \times (7^2))))} := \frac{((9 \times 8) - 64)}{(1 \times (0 + (35 + (7^2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9^{8-6}) \times 4}{(1 \times (0 + ((3^5) \times (7 \times 2))))} := \frac{(9 - 8) \times (6 \times 4)}{(1 \times (0 + ((3^5) + (7 + 2))))} := \frac{(9 - 8) \times (6 - 4)}{(1 \times (0 - (3 - ((5 + 7) \times 2))))} := \frac{(9 \times ((8 + 6) \times 4))}{(((103 + 5) \times (7^2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 \times (8 \times (6 - 4)))}{((103 + 5) \times (7 \times 2))} := \frac{(9 \times (8 + (6 - 4)))}{((10^3) - (57 - 2))} := \frac{(98 - (6 - 4))}{((10 - 3) \times ((5 + 7^2)))} := \frac{(98 - 64)}{(1 \times (0 - (3 - (5 \times 72))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.16 17 Equivalent Blocks

• Five Digit's Numerator

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10248}{97356} &:= \frac{(1^{02} + 4) \times 8}{9 + 7 \times (-3 + 56)} := \frac{(1 + 02) \times 4 + 8}{9 \times 7 \times 3 - 5 + 6} := \frac{(1 + 02) \times 4 - 8}{97 - 3 - 56} := \frac{(1 + 02 \times 4) \times 8}{(9 + 7 \times 3 \times 5) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times (02 + 4) \times 8}{9 \times (7 + 3) \times 5 + 6} := \frac{1 \times (-02 + 4 + 8)}{97 - 3 - 5 + 6} := \frac{1 \times 02 \times (4 + 8)}{9 \times (7 \times 3 + 5) - 6} := \frac{1 \times 02 \times (-4 + 8)}{97 - 3 \times 5 - 6} \\ &:= \frac{1 \times 02 + 4 + 8}{9 \times 7 \times 3 - 56} := \frac{1 \times 02 - 4 + 8}{9 + 7 + 35 + 6} := \frac{-1 \times 02 - 4 + 8}{9 + 7 - 3 \times (5 - 6)} := \frac{10 \times (2 + 4) + 8}{9 \times 73 - 5 - 6} \\ &:= \frac{10 \times (2 + 4) - 8}{(97 + 3) \times 5 - 6} := \frac{10^2 + 4 + 8}{(9 + 7 + 3) \times 56} := \frac{10 + 2 + 48}{(9 + 7 + 3) \times 5 \times 6} := \frac{10 - 2 \times (4 - 8)}{9 \times (7 - (3 - 5) \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{102 + 48}{9 - (7 - 3^5) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{= 10728}{46935} &:= \frac{(((1 - (0 - 7))^2) - 8)}{((4 - (6 - 9)) \times 35)} := \frac{((1 - (0 - (7 \times 2))) \times 8)}{(((4 \times 6) - 9) \times 35)} := \frac{((1 - (0 - 7)) \times 28)}{(4 + 6) \times (93 + 5)} := \frac{((1 - (0 - 72)) \times 8)}{((4 + 69) \times 35)} \\ &:= \frac{((10^7) \times (2 \times 8))}{(4 + (6 \times (9 - (3 - 5))))} := \frac{(((10^{7+2}) \times 8))}{(((4 + 6)^9) \times 35)} := \frac{((10 + (7 + 2)) \times 8)}{(4 + (6 + 9)) \times 35)} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (7 + (2 \times 8))))}{((4 - (6 - 9)) \times (3 \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (7 + (2^8))))}{(((4 \times 6) + 9) \times 35)} := \frac{(1 \times ((0 \times 72) + 8))}{(4 + ((6 \times (9 - 3)) - 5))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((7^2) \times 8)))}{(((4 - (6 - 9))^3) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((7 + 2) \times 8)))}{(((4 \times (6 + 9)) + 3) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((7 - 2) \times 8)))}{((4 \times ((6 + 9) \times 3)) - 5)} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (72 \times 8)))}{((4 + 6) \times (9 + (3^5)))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (72 + 8)))}{((4 + (69 - 3)) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (72 - 8)))}{(46 - (9 - (3^5)))} \\ &:= \frac{(10 \times ((7 + 2) \times 8))}{((4 + 6) \times (9 \times 35))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{13275}{84960} &:= \frac{((1 - (3 + (2 - 7))) \times 5)}{(8 \times (4 \times (9 - (6 - 0))))} := \frac{((1 - (3 - 27)) \times 5)}{(8 \times (4 + (96 - 0)))} := \frac{((1^{327}) \times 5)}{(8 - ((4 \times 9) - 60))} := \frac{((1 + ((3 + 2) \times 7)) \times 5)}{((8 + 4) \times (96 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + (3^2)) \times (7 + 5))}{(8 \times ((4 \times 9) + 60))} := \frac{((1 + (3 + 27)) \times 5)}{((8 \times 4) + 960)} := \frac{((1 + 3) \times (2 \times 75))}{((8 - 4) \times 960)} := \frac{((132 - 7) \times 5)}{((8^4) - (96 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (3 - (2 + (7 \times 5))))}{(8 + (4 \times (9 \times (6 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 - (3 - (2 + 75)))}{(8 \times (4 \times (9 + (6 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 - (3 - (27 - 5)))}{((8 \times 4) + (96 - 0))} := \frac{(1 \times (((3^2) - 7) \times 5))}{((8 - 4)^{9-6} + 0)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times ((3 + (2 \times 7)) \times 5))}{(8 - (4 - (9 \times 60)))} := \frac{(1 \times ((3 + (2^7)) \times 5))}{((8^4) + (96 - 0))} := \frac{(1 \times ((3 + (2 + 7)) \times 5))}{((8 - 4) \times (96 - 0))} := \frac{(1 \times (3 \times ((2^7) \times 5)))}{((8^4) \times (9 - (6 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (3 + (2 + 75)))}{(8 \times (4^{9-6} + 0))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{13608}{45927} &:= \frac{(((1^3) - 6) \times (0 - 8))}{(4 + (5 + (9 \times (2 \times 7))))} := \frac{(((1 + 3) \times 60) - 8)}{(((4 \times 5) + 9) \times 27)} := \frac{((1 - (3 - (6 - 0))) \times 8)}{(4 + (5 + (92 + 7)))} := \frac{((1 - (3 + 6)) \times (0 - 8))}{(4 \times (5 + ((9 - 2) \times 7)))} \\ &:= \frac{((1^{360}) \times 8)}{(4 + (5 - (9 - 27)))} := \frac{((1^3) \times (6 \times (0 + 8)))}{((4 + (5 + 9)) \times (2 + 7))} := \frac{((1^3) \times (60 \times 8))}{(4 \times (5 \times (9 \times (2 + 7))))} := \frac{((1 + (3 - 6)) \times (0 - 8))}{(4 + (5 - (9 \times (2 - 7))))} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + (36 - 0)) \times 8)}{((4^5) - ((9 \times 2) + 7))} := \frac{((1 - 3) \times (6 \times (0 - 8)))}{((45 - 9) \times (2 + 7))} := \frac{(1 \times ((3 + 60) \times 8))}{((4 + 59) \times 27)} := \frac{(1 \times ((3 - 6) \times (0 - 8)))}{(45 + (9 + 27))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (3 \times (6 \times (0 + 8))))}{((4 + (5 + 9)) \times 27)} := \frac{(1 \times (3 \times (60 \times 8)))}{(4 \times (5 \times (9 \times 27)))} := \frac{(1 \times (36 \times (0 + 8)))}{(45 + 927)} := \frac{(1 + (3 + (60 - 8)))}{((4 + (5 + (9 \times 2))) \times 7)} \\ &:= \frac{(136 + (0 - 8))}{(459 - 27)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15604}{89723} &:= \frac{(((1^5) + (6 - 0)) \times 4)}{(8 + (9 \times ((7 \times 2) + 3)))} := \frac{((1 - (5 + 6)) \times (0 - 4))}{((8 + (9 - 7)) \times 23)} := \frac{((1^5) \times (6 \times (0 + 4)))}{((8 - (9 - 7)) \times 23)} := \frac{((1^5) \times (60 + 4))}{(8 \times ((9 - 7) \times 23))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (5 + 60)) \times 4)}{(((8 \times (9 \times 7)) + 2) \times 3)} := \frac{((1 + 5) \times (60 + 4))}{((89 + 7) \times 23)} := \frac{((15 - (6 - 0)) \times 4)}{(((8 + 97) \times 2) - 3)} := \frac{((1 - 5) \times (6 \times (0 - 4)))}{(8 \times ((9 + (7 \times 2)) \times 3))} \\
 &:= \frac{((15 + (6 - 0)) \times 4)}{((89 + 72) \times 3)} := \frac{(1 - (5 + (6 \times (0 - 4))))}{((8 \times (9 + (7 - 2))) + 3)} := \frac{(1 \times ((5 + (6 - 0)) \times 4))}{(((8 \times (9 - 7))^2) - 3)} := \frac{(1 \times ((5 + 60) \times 4))}{(((8 \times 9) - 7) \times 23)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (5 - (6 + (0 - 4))))}{(8 + (9 + (7 + (2 - 3))))} := \frac{(1 + (5 + (6 - (0 \times 4))))}{(8 + (9 + ((7^2) + 3)))} := \frac{(1 + (5 + (6 - (0 - 4))))}{(8 + (9 + (72 + 3)))} := \frac{156 + 04}{897 + 23} \\
 &:= \frac{156 - 04}{897 - 23}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16092}{37548} &:= \frac{((1^6 + 0) \times (9^2))}{(3 \times (7 \times (5 - (4 - 8))))} := \frac{((1^6 + 0) + 92)}{((37 \times 5) + (4 \times 8))} := \frac{(1 \times ((6 - (0 - 9)) \times 2))}{(3 + (7 + (5 \times (4 + 8))))} := \frac{(1 \times (6 - (0 - (9 \times 2))))}{(3 - (7 - (5 \times (4 + 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (6 - (0 \times 92)))}{((3 \times 7) + (5 - (4 + 8)))} := \frac{(1 \times (6 \times ((0 \times 9) + 2)))}{(((3^7 - 5) \times 4) - 8)} := \frac{(1 \times (6 \times (0 + (9 \times 2))))}{(3 \times (7 \times ((5 \times 4) - 8)))} := \frac{(1 \times (6 \times (0 + (9 - 2))))}{(((3 + 7) \times (5 + 4)) + 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (6 \times (0 + 92)))}{(((3 \times (7 - 5))^4) - 8)} := \frac{(1 \times (6^{0 \times 9 + 2}))}{((3 \times (7 + 5)) + 48)} := \frac{(1 + (6 - ((0 \times 9) - 2)))}{(3 \times (7^5 + 4 - 8))} := \frac{(1 + (6 - (0 - (9 + 2))))}{(3 \times (7 - (5 - (4 + 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (60 - (9 - 2)))}{(3 + (75 + 48))} := \frac{(1 + (60 + (9 + 2)))}{(3 \times (7 \times ((5 - 4) \times 8)))} := \frac{(1 + (60 + 92))}{(3 \times (7 \times (5 + (4 + 8))))} := \frac{(16 - (0 - (9 + 2)))}{(3 + (7 + (5 + 48)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(160 + 92)}{(3 \times (7 \times ((5 \times 4) + 8)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17460}{39285} &:= \frac{(((1 - 7) \times 4) + 60)}{(3 - (9 - (2 + 85)))} := \frac{(((1^{74}) \times 60)}{(3 \times (9 \times (2 + (8 - 5))))} := \frac{((1 + (7 - 4)) \times (6 - 0))}{(3 + (9 + (2 + (8 \times 5))))} := \frac{((1 + 7) \times (4 \times (6 - 0)))}{(392 + (8 \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + 7) \times (46 - 0))}{(3 \times (92 \times (8 - 5)))} := \frac{((1 - 7) \times (4 - (6 - 0)))}{(3^{9 - 2 \times (8 - 5)})} := \frac{((17 \times 4) + 60)}{(3 \times (9 + (2 + 85)))} := \frac{((17 \times 4) - 60)}{(3 + (9 + (2 \times (8 - 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (7 - (4 + (6 - 0))))}{(3 \times (9 - (2 \times (8 - 5))))} := \frac{(1 - (7 - (46 - 0)))}{((3 + (9 - (2 - 8))) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 \times ((7 - 4) \times 60))}{(3 \times (9 \times (2 + (8 + 5))))} := \frac{(1 \times (7 \times (4 \times 60)))}{(3 \times (9 \times (28 \times 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (74 - (6 - 0)))}{(3 \times (9 + (2 + (8 \times 5))))} := \frac{(1 \times (74 + (6 - 0)))}{(3 + (92 + 85))} := \frac{(1 + (7 + (4 \times (6 - 0))))}{(3 \times (9 + (2 + (8 + 5))))} := \frac{(1 + (7 + (4 + 60)))}{(3 \times (9 \times (2 \times (8 - 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(174 \times (6 - 0))}{(3 \times (9 \times (2 + 85)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18390}{25746} &:= \frac{(((1^8) + 3) \times 90)}{(((2 \times 5) + 74) \times 6)} := \frac{(((1^{83}) \times 90)}{(((2^5) - (7 + 4)) \times 6)} := \frac{(((1^{83}) + (9 - 0))}{(2 - (5 - (7 + (4 + 6))))} := \frac{(((1^8) \times (3 \times 90))}{(2 + ((5 \times 74) + 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((1^8) + (39 - 0))}{(2 + (((5 + 7) \times 4) + 6))} := \frac{(((1 + (8 - 3)) \times 90)}{((2 \times 5) + 746)} := \frac{(1 - (8 - (3 + (9 - 0))))}{(25 - ((7 - 4) \times 6))} := \frac{(1 - (8 + (3 - 90)))}{(2 + (5 \times ((7 \times 4) - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((8 - 3) \times (9 - 0)))}{(2 - (5 - ((7 + 4) \times 6)))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 - (3 - 90)))}{(2 + ((5^7 - 4) + 6))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 + (3 \times (9 - 0))))}{(2 + (57 - (4 + 6)))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 + (3 + (9 - 0))))}{(2 \times (5 + (7 - (4 - 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + ((8 + 3) \times (9 - 0)))}{(2 - ((5 - (7 \times 4)) \times 6))} := \frac{(1 + (8 - (3 - (9 - 0))))}{(2 + (5 - (7 \times (4 - 6))))} := \frac{(1 + (83 - (9 - 0)))}{(2 + (57 + 46))} := \frac{(1 + (839 - 0))}{((2 + 5) \times (7 \times (4 \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(18 + (3 + (9 - 0)))}{(2 \times ((5 \times (7 - 4)) + 6))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{32508}{41796} & := \frac{(((3^2) + (5 - 0)) \times 8)}{(41 + (7 + 96))} := \frac{((3 - (2 \times 5)) \times (0 - 8))}{(4 \times ((1 - (7 - 9)) \times 6))} := \frac{((3 \times (2 \times 50)) + 8)}{((4 - (1 - (7 \times 9))) \times 6)} := \frac{((3^2) - (5 \times (0 - 8)))}{((4 + 17) \times (9 - 6))} \\
 & := \frac{((3 + (2^5 + 0)) \times 8)}{(4 \times (1 - (7 - 96)))} := \frac{((3 + (25 - 0)) \times 8)}{((4 - (1^7)) \times 96)} := \frac{((3 + 2) \times (50 - 8))}{((4 + (1^7)) \times (9 \times 6))} := \frac{((3 - 2) \times (50 - 8))}{(((4 - 1) \times (7 + 9)) + 6)} \\
 & := \frac{(3 - (2 - (5 - (0 - 8))))}{((4 \times (1 - (7 - 9))) + 6)} := \frac{(3 \times ((2 + (5 - 0)) \times 8))}{(4 \times ((1^7) \times (9 \times 6)))} := \frac{(3 \times (2 - (5 \times (0 - 8))))}{((4 - (1^7)) \times (9 \times 6))} := \frac{(3 \times (2 + (5 - (0 \times 8))))}{(4 + (1 + (7 + (9 + 6))))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 + (2^{5+0 \times 8}))}{((4 - (1^7)) \times (9 + 6))} := \frac{(3 + (2 + (50 + 8)))}{((4 - 1)^{7-9+6})} := \frac{(3 + (25 - (0 \times 8)))}{(4 \times (1 - (7 - (9 + 6))))} := \frac{(3 + (250 - 8))}{((4 + 17) \times (9 + 6))} \\
 & := \frac{(32 \times (50 - 8))}{(4 \times ((1 + 7) \times (9 \times 6)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{35784}{92016} & := \frac{(((3 \times (5 + 7)) - 8) \times 4)}{(9 \times (2 \times (0 + 16)))} := \frac{((3 \times (5 - (7 - 8))) - 4)}{((9 - (2 - (0 - 1))) \times 6)} := \frac{((3 \times (5 \times 7)) + 84)}{9^2 \times 01 \times 6} := \frac{((3 \times (5 \times 7)) - 84)}{(9 \times ((2 + (0 - 1)) \times 6))} \\
 & := \frac{((3^5) - (7 + (8 + 4)))}{(9 \times (2^{01 \times 6}))} := \frac{((3 + (5 - 7)) \times 84)}{(9 + (201 + 6))} := \frac{((35 + (7 \times 8)) \times 4)}{(920 + 16)} := \frac{((35 + 7) \times (8 + 4))}{((9^2 + 0) \times 16)} \\
 & := \frac{(3 - (5 \times (7 - (8 + 4))))}{(9 \times (2 - (0 - (1 \times 6))))} := \frac{(3 \times (5 \times (7 \times (8 - 4))))}{(9 \times (20 \times (1 \times 6)))} := \frac{(3 + ((5 \times (7 \times 8)) + 4))}{(9 + ((2 - (0 - 1))^6))} := \frac{(3 + ((5 \times 7) + (8 \times 4)))}{(9 \times (20 \times (1^6)))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 + ((5 \times 7) + (8 - 4)))}{(9 \times (2 \times (0 + (1 \times 6))))} := \frac{(35 - (7 \times (8 - 4)))}{(9 \times (2 - (0 \times 16)))} := \frac{(35 + (7 \times (8 - 4)))}{(9 \times (2 - (0 - 16)))} := \frac{(35 + (7 + 84))}{(9 \times (20 + 16))} \\
 & := \frac{(357 + 84)}{(9 \times ((20 + 1) \times 6))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{38152}{47690} & := \frac{((3 \times (8 \times 1)) + 52)}{(4 + (7 - (6 - 90)))} := \frac{((3 \times (8 \times (1^5)))^2)}{((4 + 76) \times (9 - 0))} := \frac{((3 \times (8 + (1 + 5))) + 2)}{(4 + ((7 \times 6) + (9 - 0)))} := \frac{((3 \times (8 + (1 + 5))) - 2)}{(47 - (6 - (9 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{((3 + (8 + (1 \times 5))) \times 2)}{(4 \times (7 - (6 - (9 - 0))))} := \frac{((3 + (8 + 15)) \times 2)}{(4 + (7 + (6 \times (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(3 - (8 - (1 \times (5^2))))}{(4 - (7 \times (6 - (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(3 \times ((8 \times (1 \times 5)) \times 2))}{((4^7) \times (6 + (9 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 \times (8 \times ((1 + 5) \times 2)))}{(4 \times ((7 - 6) \times 90))} := \frac{(3 \times (8 + ((1 + 5) \times 2)))}{(((4 + 7) \times 6) + (9 - 0))} := \frac{(3 \times (8 + ((1 + 5)^2)))}{((4 + 7) \times (6 + (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 + (8 - (1 \times (5 + 2))))}{(4 + ((7 - 6)^9 + 0))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 + (8 + (1 \times (5^2))))}{((4 + (7 - 6)) \times (9 - 0))} := \frac{(3 + (8 + (1 + 52)))}{(4 + (7 + (69 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 + (8 + (15^2)))}{((4 \times 76) - (9 - 0))} := \frac{(3 + (81 + 52))}{(4 + (76 + 90))} \\
 & := \frac{(381 + (5 + 2))}{(476 + (9 - 0))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{47016}{52893} & := \frac{((4 \times (7 - (0 - 1)))^6)}{((5 - 2) \times ((8^9) \times 3))} := \frac{((4 \times 70) - 16)}{(5 + (289 + 3))} := \frac{((4 + (7 - (0 - 1))) \times 6)}{(((5 \times 2) + (8 + 9)) \times 3)} := \frac{((4 + (7 - 0)) \times 16)}{((5 + 28) \times (9 - 3))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times ((7 - (0 - 1)) \times 6))}{((5 + (2 + (8 - 9)))^3)} := \frac{(4 \times (7 - (0 - (1^6))))}{(5 + ((2 \times (8 + 9)) - 3))} := \frac{(4 \times (7 - (0 - (1 + 6))))}{((5 \times (2 - 8)) + 93)} := \frac{(4 \times (7 - (0 - (1 - 6))))}{(5 + (2^{8-9+3}))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times (7 \times (0 + (1 \times 6))))}{(5 + (2 \times (89 + 3)))} := \frac{(4 \times (7 + (0 - (1^6))))}{(5 + (2 + (8 + (9 + 3))))} := \frac{(4 \times (7 + (0 - (1 - 6))))}{(5 - (2 - ((8 + 9) \times 3))} := \frac{(4 \times (70 - (1 \times 6)))}{((5 + (2 + 89)) \times 3)} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times (70 + (1 \times 6)))}{(((5^2) + 89) \times 3)} := \frac{(4^{7+01-6})}{((5 \times (2 - (8 - 9))) + 3)} := \frac{(4 + ((7 + (0 - 1)) \times 6))}{(5 + (2 \times (8 + (9 + 3))))} := \frac{(4 + (70 + (1 \times 6)))}{((5 + (2 + 8)) \times (9 - 3))} \\
 & := \frac{(470 - (1 \times 6))}{(528 - (9 - 3))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{63504}{91728} &:= \frac{((6+3) \times (5 - (0 - 4)))}{(9 \times (1 \times (7 - (2 - 8))))} := \frac{((6+3) \times (5 \times (0 + 4)))}{((9 + 17) \times (2 + 8))} := \frac{((6+3) \times 504)}{(9 \times (1 \times 728))} := \frac{(6 \times (3 \times (5 - (0 \times 4))))}{((9 + 1) \times (7 - (2 - 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times (3 \times (5 - (0 - 4))))}{(9 \times ((17 \times 2) - 8))} := \frac{(6 \times (3 \times (5 \times (0 + 4))))}{(((9 \times (1 \times 7)) + 2) \times 8)} := \frac{(6 \times (3 + (5 - (0 - 4))))}{((9 - (1 - (7 - 2))) \times 8)} := \frac{(6^{3-5+04})}{(9 + (1 - (7 \times (2 - 8))))} \\ &:= \frac{6^3 \times (5 - 04)}{(((9 - 1) \times 7) + (2^8))} := \frac{(6 + (3^{5-04}))}{(9 + (1 - (7 - (2 + 8))))} := \frac{(6 + (3 + (5 - (0 - 4))))}{(9 + (1 \times (7 + (2 + 8))))} := \frac{(6 + (3 + (50 + 4)))}{((9 \times (1 \times 7)) + 28)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + (35 - (0 - 4)))}{(9 - (1 - ((7^2) + 8)))} := \frac{(63 - (5 - (0 - 4)))}{(9 - (1 - (7 \times (2 + 8))))} := \frac{(63 \times (5 - (0 - 4)))}{(91 + 728)} := \frac{(63 + (50 + 4))}{((9 \times 17) + (2 \times 8))} \\ &:= \frac{(635 - (0 - 4))}{(917 - (2 - 8))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{70254}{81963} &:= \frac{(((7^{02}) + 5) \times 4)}{((81 + (9 - 6)) \times 3)} := \frac{(((7 - (0 - 2)) \times 54)}{((8 + (1^9)) \times 63)} := \frac{(((7 \times (0 \times 2)) + 54)}{(8 + (1 - (9 - 63)))} := \frac{(((7 \times (0 + (2 \times 5))) - 4)}{((8 \times (1 + 9)) - (6 - 3))} \\ &:= \frac{((7^{02}) - (5 - 4))}{(8 \times (1 + (9 - (6 - 3))))} := \frac{(((7 + (0 - 2)) \times 54)}{((8 + (1 + 96)) \times 3)} := \frac{(((70 + 2) \times 54)}{(8 \times (1 \times (9 \times 63)))} := \frac{(7 - (0 - (2 + (5 + 4))))}{(8 + (1 + (9 + (6 - 3))))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 - (0 - (25 + 4)))}{((8 + ((1^9) \times 6)) \times 3)} := \frac{(7 \times ((0 \times 2) + 54))}{((8 - (1^9)) \times 63)} := \frac{(7 \times (0 - ((2 - 5) \times 4)))}{(8 + ((1 + 9) \times (6 + 3)))} := \frac{(7 \times (0 + (2 \times 54)))}{(819 + 63)} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + (0 - (2 - (5 - 4))))}{(8 - (1^{963}))} := \frac{(70 - (2 \times (5 \times 4)))}{(8 + (1 \times (9 \times (6 - 3))))} := \frac{(70 + (2 \times (5 - 4)))}{((8 - 1) \times (9 + (6 - 3)))} := \frac{(702 \times (5 + 4))}{(819 \times (6 + 3))} \\ &:= \frac{(702 - 54)}{(819 - 63)} \end{aligned}$$

• Four Digit's Numerator

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1935}{247680} &:= \frac{(((1^9) + 3) \times 5)}{((2^{4+7-6}) \times 80)} := \frac{(((1^9) + 3)^5)}{(2 \times (4^{(7-6) \times (8-0)}))} := \frac{((1^{93}) \times 5)}{(2 \times (4 \times ((7 - 6) \times 80)))} := \frac{((1^{93}) + 5)}{(2 \times ((4 \times 76) + 80))} \\ &:= \frac{((1^9) - (3 - 5))}{((2 + (4 + (7 \times 6))) \times (8 - 0))} := \frac{((1^9) \times (3 \times 5))}{((2 + ((4 \times 7) - 6)) \times 80)} := \frac{((1^9) + (3 \times 5))}{(2 \times (4^{7+6-8+0}))} := \frac{((1^9) + 35)}{((2 + 4) \times (768 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + (9 + 3)) \times 5)}{(2 \times (4 \times ((7 + 6) \times 80)))} := \frac{((19 - 3)^5)}{((2 \times 4)^{7-6+8+0})} := \frac{(1 \times ((9 - 3) \times 5))}{((2 + (4 + (7 \times 6))) \times 80)} := \frac{(1^{935})}{((2^4 \times (7-6)) \times (8 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (9 - (3 + 5)))}{(2^{4-76+80})} := \frac{(1 + (9 + (3 \times 5)))}{((2 - (4 - (7 \times 6))) \times 80)} := \frac{(19 - (3 \times 5))}{(2^{4+7+6-8+0})} := \frac{(19 - (3 - 5))}{(2 \times (4 \times (7 \times (6 \times (8 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(19 \times (3 \times 5))}{((2 + 4) \times (76 \times 80))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{2304}{158976} &:= \frac{((2 \times (3 - 0)) + 4)}{((1 - (5 - ((8 + 9) \times 7))) \times 6)} := \frac{((2^3 + 0) \times 4)}{((1 + ((5 \times (8 \times 9)) + 7)) \times 6)} := \frac{((2^3 + 0) + 4)}{((1 + ((5 \times 8) + 97)) \times 6)} := \frac{((2^3 + 0) - 4)}{((1 - (5 - 8)) \times ((9 \times 7) + 6))} \\ &:= \frac{((2 + (3 - 0)) \times 4)}{((158 \times 9) - (7 \times 6))} := \frac{(2 - (3 \times (0 \times 4)))}{((15 - (8 - (9 + 7))) \times 6)} := \frac{(2 - (3 + (0 - 4)))}{((15 + 8) \times (9 \times (7 - 6)))} := \frac{(2 \times (3 - (0 \times 4)))}{(1 + (5 + (8 \times (9 + (7 \times 6))))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (3 - (0 - 4)))}{((1 + (5 + (8 + 9))) \times (7 \times 6))} := \frac{(2 \times (3 \times (0 + 4)))}{((1 - (5 \times (8 - (9 \times 7)))) \times 6)} := \frac{(2 \times (30 + 4))}{((1 + (5 + (8 \times 97))) \times 6)} := \frac{(2^{3-0 \times 4})}{((1 - (5 - (89 + 7))) \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (3 - (0 \times 4)))}{(15 - ((8 - (9 \times 7)) \times 6))} := \frac{(2 + (3 - (0 - 4)))}{(((1^5) + 8) \times ((9 \times 7) + 6))} := \frac{(2 + (3 + (0 - 4)))}{(1 \times (5 + (8 \times (9 - (7 - 6)))))} := \frac{(23 - (0 \times 4))}{((15 + 8) \times ((9 \times 7) + 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(23 + (0 - 4))}{((15 + 8) \times ((9 \times 7) - 6))} \end{aligned}$$

$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{3798}{102546} &:= \frac{((3 \times 7) + 9) \times 8}{(10 \times (2 \times (54 \times 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{((3 \times 7) - (9 + 8))}{(1 \times (0 + (2 \times ((5 + 4) \times 6))))} \\ &:= \frac{((3 + (7 - 9)) \times 8)}{(1 \times (0 + (((2^5) + 4) \times 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (7 + (9 - 8)))}{(1 \times (0 + (2 \times (54 \times 6))))} \\ &:= \frac{(37 - (9 - 8))}{((1 - (0 - 2)) \times (54 \times 6))} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(((3 \times 7) - 9) \times 8)}{((10 - 2) \times (54 \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{((3 \times 7) + (9 - 8))}{(((10^2) - (5 - 4)) \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{((3 + (7 - 9))^8)}{(1 \times (0 - (2 - (5 + (4 \times 6)))))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (7 \times (9 - 8)))}{(10 \times (25 - (4 - 6)))} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{((3 - (7 - 9)) \times 8)}{(10 \times (2 \times ((5 + 4) \times 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{((3^7) \times (9 \times 8))}{((10 - 2) \times ((5 + 4)^6))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (7 - (9 - 8)))}{(1 \times (((0 - (2 - 5))^4) \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (7 + (9 + 8)))}{((1 - (0 - (2 \times (5 - 4))))^6)} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{((3 \times (7 - 9)) + 8)}{(1 - (0 - (2 + (5 + 46))))} \\ &:= \frac{((3 + (7 + 9)) \times 8)}{(1 - (0 - (2 + (5 + (4^6)))))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (7 + (9 + 8)))}{(((10 \times (2^5)) + 4) \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (79 + 8))}{(((1 - (0 - 2))^5) \times (4 + 6))} \end{aligned}$
$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4137}{268905} &:= \frac{(((4 + 1)^3) + 7)}{(2 \times (6 \times ((8 \times 90) - 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{((4 \times (1 + 3))^7)}{(26 \times ((8^9 + 0) \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - (1 + (3 - 7)))}{(((2 + (6 \times 8)) \times (9 - 0)) + 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (1 - (3 - 7)))}{(2 + ((6 \times (8 + 90)) - 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (1 + (3 - 7)))}{((2 - (6 - (8 + (9 - 0)))) \times 5)} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(((4 - 1) \times 3) + 7)}{(2 \times ((6 + (8 + 90)) \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{((4 + (1 + 3)) \times 7)}{((2 + (6 + (8 \times 90))) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (1 + (3 \times 7)))}{(((2 + 6) \times ((8 \times 90) - 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (1 \times (3 \times 7)))}{(((26 - 8) \times 90) + 5)} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(((4 - 1) \times 3) - 7)}{(26 \times ((8 - 9) \times (0 - 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - ((1^3)^7))}{((2 \times (6 + (89 - 0))) + 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + ((1^3)^7))}{(((2^6) - (8 - (9 - 0))) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (1 \times (3 + 7)))}{((2 - ((6 - 8) \times 90)) \times 5)} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(((4 - 1)^3) + 7)}{(26 \times ((8 + (9 - 0)) \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - (1 \times (3 - 7)))}{((2 + (6 \times (8 + (9 - 0)))) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + ((1^3) + 7))}{(2 \times ((6 + (8 \times (9 - 0))) \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (1 + (3 + 7)))}{(2 + (68 + 905))} \end{aligned}$
$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4806}{153792} &:= \frac{((4 \times (8 - 0)) + 6)}{(1 + (5 \times (3 \times (79 + 2))))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - (8 \times (0 - 6)))}{(1 + ((5 \times (37 \times 9)) - 2))} \\ &:= \frac{(4^{8+0 \times 6})}{(((1^{53}) + 7)^{9-2})} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + (0 - 6)))}{((1 + (5 \times (3 + (7 + 9)))) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{(480 + 6)}{(((1 + 5)^{3-7+9}) \times 2)} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{((4 + (8 - 0)) \times 6)}{(1 \times (((5 - 3)^7) \times (9 \times 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - (8 + (0 - 6)))}{(1 - ((5 \times (3 - (7 + 9)))) + 2)} \\ &:= \frac{(4^{8-06})}{(1 \times ((5 - 3) \times ((7 + 9)^2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (80 + 6))}{((153 + 7) \times (9 \times 2))} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{((4 - 8) \times (0 - 6))}{(1 \times ((5 + 379) \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (8 - (0 \times 6)))}{((1 - (5 + ((3 - 7) \times 9)))^2)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (8 - (0 \times 6)))}{(1 + (5 + (3 \times (7 \times (9 \times 2)))))} \\ &:= \frac{(48 - (0 - 6))}{((1 + 53) \times ((7 + 9) \times 2))} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4 - (8 \times (0 \times 6)))}{(1 \times (5 - (3 - (7 \times (9 \times 2)))))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (8 + (0 - 6)))}{((1 + ((5^3) - (7 - 9))) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (8 - (0 - 6)))}{(1 + (5 + (3 + (7 \times (9^2)))))} \\ &:= \frac{(48 \times (0 + 6))}{((1 + (5 \times (3 + (7 + 9))))^2)} \end{aligned}$
$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{6093}{274185} &:= \frac{((6 \times (0 + 9)) + 3)}{(((2^7) \times 4) + (1^8)) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - (0 - (9 + 3)))}{(2 \times ((74 - (1 - 8)) \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times (0 + (9^3)))}{(2 \times (((7 - 4) \times (1 + 8)) \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + ((0 \times 9) - 3))}{(2 - (7 \times (4 - (18 + 5))))} \\ &:= \frac{(60 + 93)}{(27 \times ((4 - 1) \times 85))} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{((6 \times (0 + 9)) - 3)}{((2 + 7) \times ((4 - 1) \times 85))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - (0 - (9 - 3)))}{(2 \times ((7 - 4) \times (18 \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times (0 + (9 + 3)))}{(27 \times ((4 - 1) \times (8 \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(60 - (9 + 3))}{(2 \times (((7 \times 4) - 1) \times (8 \times 5)))} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(6 - ((0 \times 9) - 3))}{((2 + (7 + (4 \times 18))) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - (0 \times 93))}{(2 \times (((7 \times (4 + 1)) - 8) \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times (0 + (9 - 3)))}{(27 \times ((4 + (1 \times 8)) \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(60 - (9 - 3))}{(27 \times (4 + (1 + 85)))} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(6 - (0 - (9 \times 3)))}{((2 + ((7 \times 41) + 8)) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - (0 - 93))}{(27 \times ((41 - 8) \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(6^{0 \times 9 + 3})}{(27 \times (4 \times (18 \times 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{(60 + (9 - 3))}{((2 + (74 \times (1 \times 8))) \times 5)} \end{aligned}$
$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8027}{136459} &:= \frac{((8 \times (0 \times 2)) + 7)}{(((1 - (3 - (6 \times 4))) \times 5) + 9)} \\ &:= \frac{((8^0) - 7)}{(1 \times ((3 \times (64 \times 5)) + 9))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 - (0 - (2 + 7)))}{(1 - (3 \times (6 \times (4 \times (5 - 9)))))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 \times ((0 \times 2) + 7))}{(1 + ((3 \times (64 \times 5)) - 9))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 + (0 - (2 - 7)))}{(13 \times (6 + ((4 \times 5) - 9)))} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{((8 \times (0 + 2)) + 7)}{(13 + (6 \times (4 + 59)))} \\ &:= \frac{((8 + (0 - 2)) \times 7)}{(1 + ((3^6) + (4 \times (5 - 9))))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 - (0 - (2 - 7)))}{(1 \times (3 + (6 \times (4 - (5 - 9)))))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 \times (0 - (2 - 7)))}{(1 \times ((3^6) - (4 + (5 \times 9))))} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{((8 \times (0 + 2)) - 7)}{(1 \times ((3 \times (6 \times (4 + 5))) - 9))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 - ((0 \times 2) - 7))}{(1 + ((3 \times 6) + (4 \times 59)))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 - (0 \times 27))}{(1 + (3 \times ((6 + (4 - 5)) \times 9)))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 \times (0 + (2 + 7)))}{((1 + ((3 + (6 \times 4)) \times 5)) \times 9)} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{((8^0) \times 7)}{(136 \times (4 \times (5 + 9)))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 - (0 - (2 \times 7)))}{(((1 + (3 \times (6 \times 4))) \times 5) + 9)} \\ &:= \frac{(8 - (0 - 27))}{(1 - ((3 - (64 + 5)) \times 9))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 + ((0 \times 2) - 7))}{(1 \times (3 + (6 + (4 - (5 - 9)))))} \end{aligned}$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9046}{153782} &:= \frac{((9 \times (0 \times 4)) + 6)}{((1 + (5 + (3 \times (7 + 8)))) \times 2)} := \frac{((9 \times (0 + 4)) + 6)}{((1 + ((5^3) - 7)) \times (8 - 2))} := \frac{((9 + (0 - 4)) \times 6)}{((1 + (5 \times (3 + 7))) \times (8 + 2))} := \frac{(9 - ((0 \times 4) - 6))}{(1 \times (5 \times (3 \times (7 + (8 + 2))))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 - (0 - (4 \times 6)))}{(1 + ((5 + 3) \times (7 \times (8 + 2))))} := \frac{(9 - (0 - (4 - 6)))}{(1 + (((5 + (3 + 7)) \times 8) - 2))} := \frac{(9 - (0 \times 46))}{(1 - ((5 - (3 + 78)) \times 2))} := \frac{(9 - (0 - 46))}{(153 + 782)} \\ &:= \frac{(9 \times ((0 \times 4) + 6))}{((1 + 53) \times (7 + (8 + 2)))} := \frac{(9 \times (0 - (4 - 6)))}{(1 + (5 \times (3 + ((7 \times 8) + 2))))} := \frac{(9 \times (0 + (4 \times 6)))}{(((1 + 5)^3) \times (7 + (8 + 2)))} := \frac{(9 \times (0 + 46))}{((1 + (5 + 3)) \times 782)} \\ &:= \frac{(9 + ((0 \times 4) - 6))}{(1 - (5 \times (3 - (7 + (8 - 2)))))} := \frac{(9 + (0 - (4 - 6)))}{(1 \times ((5 \times (3 \times 7)) + 82))} := \frac{(90 - (4 - 6))}{(1 \times ((5 - 3) \times 782))} := \frac{(90 + (4 - 6))}{(((1 + 5)^3) \times 7) - (8 \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{(90 - 46)}{((1 - (5 - 378)) \times 2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9765}{214830} &:= \frac{(((9 - 7) \times 6) - 5)}{(2 + (1 \times (4 \times (8 + 30))))} := \frac{((9 \times 7) - (6 \times 5))}{(214 + (8^3 + 0))} := \frac{((9 - 7) \times (6 \times 5))}{(2 \times ((14 + 8) \times 30))} := \frac{((9 - 7) \times (6 + 5))}{(2 - (1 - (483 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 - ((7 - 6) \times 5))}{(2 \times (1 \times (4 \times (8 + (3 - 0)))))} := \frac{(9 - ((7 - 6)^5))}{(2 \times (1 + (4 + (83 - 0))))} := \frac{(9 - (7 - (6 + 5)))}{2^{14} \times 8 + 30} := \frac{(9 - (7 - (6 - 5)))}{((2 \times (1 \times 48)) - 30)} \\ &:= \frac{(9 - (7 \times (6 - 5)))}{(2 + (1 \times (4 + (8 + 30))))} := \frac{(9 - (7 + (6 - 5)))}{(2 + (1 \times (4 \times (8 - (3 - 0)))))} := \frac{(9 \times ((7 - 6) \times 5))}{((2 - (1 - (4 \times 8))) \times 30)} := \frac{(9^{(7-6)^5})}{(2 \times ((1 + (4 \times 8)) \times (3 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 + ((7 - 6) \times 5))}{(2 \times (14 \times (8 + (3 - 0))))} := \frac{(9 + (7 - (6 + 5)))}{(2 \times ((1 + 4) \times (8 + (3 - 0))))} := \frac{(9 + (7 - (6 - 5)))}{((2 + ((1^4) + 8)) \times 30)} := \frac{(9 + (7 \times (6 - 5)))}{((2 \times (1 + 4)) \times (8 + (3 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 + (76 + 5))}{(2 \times ((1 + (4 \times 8)) \times 30))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9846}{123075} &:= \frac{(((9 - 8)^4) \times 6)}{(1 + (2 - (3 + (0 - 75))))} := \frac{((9 - (8 - 4)) \times 6)}{((1 + (2 \times (30 + 7))) \times 5)} := \frac{((9 \times (8 - 4)) + 6)}{((1 + (2 \times (3 - 0))) \times 75)} := \frac{((9 \times 8) - (4 \times 6))}{(1 \times ((2^3 + 0) \times 75))} \\ &:= \frac{((9 \times 8) + (4 + 6))}{(1 + ((2 + 30)^{7-5}))} := \frac{((9 \times 8) - 46)}{((12 \times 30) - (7 \times 5))} := \frac{((9 + (8 \times 4)) \times 6)}{((1 + (2 \times 307)) \times 5)} := \frac{((9 - 8) \times (4 \times 6))}{((1 - (2 + 3)) \times (0 - 75))} \\ &:= \frac{((9 - 8) \times (4 + 6))}{(1 \times ((2 + (30 - 7)) \times 5))} := \frac{(9 \times ((8 + 4) \times 6))}{(((1 + 2) \times 30)^{7-5})} := \frac{(9 \times ((8 - 4) \times 6))}{(12 \times (3 \times (0 + 75)))} := \frac{(9 \times (8 - (4 - 6)))}{((1 + ((2 + 30) \times 7)) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(9 \times (8 + (4 \times 6)))}{(1 \times ((2 \times 30)^{7-5}))} := \frac{(9 \times (8 + (4 + 6)))}{(((1 + 2)^3 + 0) \times 75)} := \frac{(9 \times (8 + (4 - 6)))}{((1 + (2^3 + 0)) \times 75)} := \frac{(98 + 46)}{(1 \times (2 \times (30^{7-5})))} \\ &:= \frac{(98 - 46)}{((123 - (0 - 7)) \times 5)} \end{aligned}$$

3.17 18 Equivalent Blocks

• Five Digit's Numerator

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10345}{26897} &:= \frac{(((1 - (0 - 3))^4) \times 5)}{(26 \times (8 \times (9 + 7)))} := \frac{(((1^{03}) + 4) \times 5)}{(((2 - 6) \times 8) + 97)} := \frac{((1 - (0 - (3 \times 4))) \times 5)}{(((26 - 8) \times 9) + 7)} \\ &:= \frac{((1 - (0 - 34)) \times 5)}{(((2^6) - (8 - 9)) \times 7)} := \frac{((1^{03}) \times (4 \times 5))}{(2 + ((6 \times 8) + (9 - 7)))} := \frac{((1^{03}) \times 45)}{((2 \times 6) + (8 + 97))} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + (0 - (3 - 4))) \times 5)}{(2 \times (6 - ((8 - 9) \times 7)))} := \frac{((10 - (3 - 4)) \times 5)}{((2^6) + ((8 \times 9) + 7))} := \frac{((10 \times (3 \times 4)) - 5)}{(((26 + 8) \times 9) - 7)} \\ &:= \frac{((10 \times 34) - 5)}{((2 \times (6 \times (8 \times 9))) + 7)} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (3 - (4 - 5))))}{(2 - (((6 - 8) \times 9) + 7))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (34 + 5)))}{(2 + (6 + (89 + 7)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (34 - 5)))}{(2 - (6 - (89 - 7)))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((3 + 4) \times 5)))}{((2 - (6 - (8 + 9))) \times 7)} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (3 \times (4 \times 5))))}{(26 \times (8 - (9 - 7)))} \\ &:= \frac{(10 - ((3 - 4) \times 5))}{((2^{6+8-9}) + 7)} := \frac{(10^{3+4-5})}{(26 \times (8 + (9 - 7)))} := \frac{(10 + 345)}{(26 + 897)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10536}{28974} &:= \frac{((1 - (0 - (5 \times 3))) \times 6)}{((2 + (8^{9-7})) \times 4)} := \frac{((1^{05}) \times 36)}{((2 \times 8) + (9 + 74))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - ((5^3) + 6)))}{(289 + 74)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - ((5^3) - 6)))}{(2 + ((89 - 7) \times 4))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 + (3 \times 6))))}{(2 + (8 \times ((9 - 7) \times 4)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (53 + 6)))}{(2 + (89 + 74))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (53 - 6)))}{((2 \times (8^{9-7})) + 4)} := \frac{(1 \times (0 - (5 - (3 + 6))))}{((2 + (8 - 9)) \times (7 + 4))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((5 - 3) \times 6)))}{((2 - (8 - 9)) \times (7 + 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((5 - 3)^6)))}{((28 + (9 + 7)) \times 4)} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (5 - (3 - 6))))}{(2 + (8 + (9 + (7 - 4))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + 536))}{(2 \times (8 + (9^{7-4})))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (5 \times (3 - 6))))}{((2 \times (8 + (9 + 7))) - 4)} := \frac{(1 + (0 - (5 - 36)))}{(2 + (89 - (7 - 4)))} := \frac{(10 \times ((5 - 3)^6))}{((28 \times (9 \times 7)) - 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 \times (5 \times (3 \times 6)))}{(2 + ((8 \times 9) + (7^4)))} := \frac{(10 \times (5 + (3 - 6)))}{(28 + (9 \times (7 - 4)))} := \frac{(10^{5+3-6})}{((2^8) - (9 - (7 \times 4)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14796}{30825} &:= \frac{(((1 + 4) \times 7) + 9) \times 6}{((30 - 8) \times 25)} := \frac{(((1^4) + 7) \times (9 \times 6))}{(30 \times ((8 - 2) \times 5))} := \frac{((1 - ((4 - 7) \times 9)) \times 6)}{(30 + ((8^2) \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 - (4 - 7)) \times (9 \times 6))}{(30 \times (8 + (2 + 5)))} := \frac{((1 - (4 - 79)) \times 6)}{((30 + 8) \times 25)} := \frac{((1^4) - (7 - (9 \times 6)))}{((30 - (8 + 2)) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (4 + 7)) \times 96)}{(30 \times (8 \times (2 \times 5)))} := \frac{((1 + 47) \times (9 + 6))}{(30 \times ((8 + 2) \times 5))} := \frac{((1 + 47) \times 96)}{(30 \times ((8^2) \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + 479) \times 6)}{(30 \times (8 \times 25))} := \frac{((14 - (7 - 9)) \times 6)}{((30 + (8 + 2)) \times 5)} := \frac{((14 + (7 - 9)) \times 6)}{(3 \times (0 + ((8 + 2) \times 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((4 - (7 - 9)) \times 6))}{(3 \times ((0 \times 8) + 25))} := \frac{(1 \times ((4 + (7 + 9)) \times 6))}{((30 \times 8) + (2 \times 5))} := \frac{(1 \times (4 - (7 - (9 + 6))))}{((3 \times (0 + (8 + 2))) - 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 \times ((7 \times 9) - 6)))}{((30 \times (8 \times 2)) - 5)} := \frac{(1 \times (4 \times (7 \times (9 - 6))))}{((30 \times (8 - 2)) - 5)} := \frac{(147 - (9 + 6))}{((3 - (0 - 8)) \times 25)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{47628} &:= \frac{(((1 + 5)^3 + 0) + 9)}{(4 \times (7 + (6 \times 28)))} := \frac{(((1 + 5)^3 + 0) - 9)}{(4 \times (((7 + 6)^2) - 8))} := \frac{((1 + (5 \times (3 - 0))) \times 9)}{(4 \times (7 \times (6 + (2 + 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (53 - 0)) \times 9)}{(4 \times (7 \times (62 - 8)))} := \frac{((15 - (3 - 0)) \times 9)}{(4 \times (7 \times (6 - (2 - 8))))} := \frac{((15 + (3 - 0)) \times 9)}{(476 + 28)} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 - 53) \times (0 - 9))}{(4 \times ((7 + 6) \times 28))} := \frac{(1 \times (53 \times (0 + 9)))}{((47 + 6) \times 28)} := \frac{(1 + (5 + (3 - (0 \times 9))))}{(4 \times (7 - (6 + (2 - 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (5 + (3 - (0 - 9))))}{((4^{7-6+2}) - 8)} := \frac{(1 + (5 + (30 + 9)))}{(4 \times (7 + ((6^2) - 8)))} := \frac{(1 + (5 + (30 - 9)))}{((4 \times (7 + (6 \times 2))) + 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (53 - (0 \times 9)))}{(((4 + 76) \times 2) + 8)} := \frac{(1 + (53 - (0 - 9)))}{((4 \times (7 \times 6)) + 28)} := \frac{(1 + (530 + 9))}{(4 \times (7 \times (6 \times (2 + 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(15 \times (3 - (0 - 9)))}{(4 \times (7 \times ((6 \times 2) + 8)))} := \frac{(15 + (30 - 9))}{(4 \times (7 \times ((6 \times 2) - 8)))} := \frac{(153 - (0 \times 9))}{((4 + (7 + 6)) \times 28)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15309}{78246} &:= \frac{(((1+5)^3 + 0) - 9)}{((7 + (8 \times 2)) \times 46)} &:= \frac{((1^5) \times (30 \times 9))}{((7 + 8) \times (2 \times 46))} &:= \frac{((1 + (5 \times (3 - 0))) \times 9)}{(782 - 46)} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (5 + (3 - 0))) \times 9)}{((7 \times ((8^2) - 4)) - 6)} &:= \frac{((1 + (53 - 0)) \times 9)}{(((7 \times 8) - 2) \times 46)} &:= \frac{((15 - (3 - 0)) \times 9)}{((7 \times (82 - 4)) + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{((15 \times 30) - 9)}{(7 \times ((82 \times 4) - 6))} &:= \frac{((15 + (3 - 0)) \times 9)}{(782 + 46)} &:= \frac{(1 + ((5^3 + 0) - 9))}{((7 \times 82) + (4 \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{1 + 5^{3+0 \times 9}}{(7 \times (82 + (4 + 6)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (5 + (3 - (0 \times 9))))}{((7 - (8 - 2)) \times 46)} &:= \frac{(1 + (5 + (3 - (0 - 9))))}{((7 \times (8 + (2 + 4))) - 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (5 + (30 + 9)))}{((7 \times (8 + 24)) + 6)} &:= \frac{(1 + (5 + (30 - 9)))}{((7 - (8 - 24)) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(1 + (53 - (0 \times 9)))}{(((7 \times (8 - 2)) + 4) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (53 - (0 - 9)))}{(7 \times (((8 + 2) \times 4) + 6))} &:= \frac{(1 + (530 - 9))}{(((7 \times 8) + 2) \times 46)} &:= \frac{(153 - (0 \times 9))}{((7 + (8 + 2)) \times 46)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16905}{74382} &:= \frac{((1^6) \times (9 \times (0 + 5)))}{((7 \times (4 + (3 \times 8))) + 2)} &:= \frac{((1^6) + (9 + (0 - 5)))}{(7 - (4 - (3 + (8 \times 2))))} &:= \frac{((16 - (9 - 0)) \times 5)}{(7 \times (4 + (3 \times (8 - 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((16 \times 90) - 5)}{((74 + 3) \times 82)} &:= \frac{(1 - (6 - (90 + 5)))}{((7 + 4) \times (38 - 2))} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((6 \times 90) + 5))}{((7^4) + (3 - (8 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((6 + (9 - 0)) \times 5))}{((7 + 4) \times (3 \times (8 + 2)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((6 + 90) \times 5))}{((7 + 4) \times (3 \times (8^2)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (6 + (9 - (0 \times 5))))}{(7 + (43 + (8 \times 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (6 + (9 + 05)))}{(7 - (4 - (3 + 82)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (6 + (9 + (0 - 5))))}{((7 + (4 + (3 + 8))) \times 2)} &:= \frac{(1 \times (69 \times (0 + 5)))}{(74 + (38^2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + ((6 \times (9 - 0)) - 5))}{((7 \times 4) + (3 \times (8^2)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (6 \times (9 - (0 \times 5))))}{((7 + 4) \times ((3 + 8) \times 2))} &:= \frac{(1 + (6 \times (9 + (0 - 5))))}{(((7 + (4 + 3)) \times 8) - 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (69 - (0 \times 5)))}{(7 \times (4 + (38 + 2)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (69 + (0 - 5)))}{((74 \times 3) + (8^2))} &:= \frac{(16 + (9 + 05))}{(7 + (4 + ((3 + 8)^2)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{19068}{52437} &:= \frac{(((1^9 + 0) + 6) \times 8)}{(((5 \times 2) + (4 \times 3)) \times 7)} &:= \frac{((1 - (9 - 0)) \times (6 - 8))}{(5 - (2 - (4 + 37)))} &:= \frac{((1^9 + 0) \times (6 \times 8))}{((5^2 + 4 - 3) + 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{((1^9 + 0) \times 68)}{((52 \times 4) - (3 \times 7))} &:= \frac{((1 + (9 + (0 - 6))) \times 8)}{((5 \times ((2^4) + 3)) - 7)} &:= \frac{((1 + (9 - 0)) \times (6 + 8))}{(5 \times (((2 \times 4) + 3) \times 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + 9) \times (0 - (6 - 8)))}{(5 + (2 \times (4 + (3 \times 7))))} &:= \frac{((1 + 9)^{-06+8})}{(5 \times (((2^4) \times 3) + 7))} &:= \frac{((1 - 9) \times (0 - (6 + 8)))}{(5 + (2 + (43 \times 7)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (9 + (0 - (6 \times 8))))}{((5 \times 24) - (3 + 7))} &:= \frac{(1 - (9 + (0 - 68)))}{(5 + ((2^4) \times (3 + 7)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (9 \times ((0 \times 6) + 8)))}{((52 \times 4) - (3 + 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (90 - (6 + 8)))}{(((5 \times 2) - 4)^3 - 7)} &:= \frac{(1 + (9 - (0 - (6 + 8))))}{(5 + (24 + 37))} &:= \frac{(1 + (9 - (0 - (6 - 8))))}{((5 \times (2 + (4 - 3))) + 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (9 + (0 - (6 - 8))))}{(5 + (2 \times (4 + (3 + 7))))} &:= \frac{190 - 6 + 8}{524 - 3 + 7} &:= \frac{190 + 6 + 8}{524 + 37}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20169}{78435} &:= \frac{(((2 - (0 - 1))^6) + 9)}{((78 + 4) \times 35)} := \frac{(((2 \times (0 - 1)) + 6) \times 9)}{(7 \times (8 + (4 + (3 + 5))))} := \frac{((2 - (0 - (1 + 6))) \times 9)}{((7 - (8 - (4^3))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 - (0 - 1)) \times (6 + 9))}{(7 \times (8 + ((4 \times 3) + 5)))} := \frac{((2^{01 \times 6}) \times 9)}{(7 \times (((8 - 4)^3) \times 5))} := \frac{((2 + (0 - (1 - 6))) \times 9)}{(7 \times ((8 - (4 - 3)) \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + (0 - 1)) \times (6 \times 9))}{((7 - (8 - 43)) \times 5)} := \frac{((20 + (1 - 6)) \times 9)}{(7 \times ((8 + (4 + 3)) \times 5))} := \frac{((20 + 1) \times (6 + 9))}{(7 \times (((8 \times 4) + 3) \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((20 + 16) \times 9)}{(7 \times ((8 + 4) \times (3 \times 5)))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (1 + (6 + 9))))}{(7 \times (8 + (4 + (3 - 5))))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (1 + 69)))}{(7 \times (8 + (4 \times (3 + 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (16 + 9)))}{(7 \times (8 + ((4 \times 3) - 5)))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (16 - 9)))}{(7 \times ((8 - (4 + 3)) \times 5))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - 169))}{((7 + (8 + 4)) \times 35)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (1 \times (6 \times 9))))}{(7 \times ((8 - 4) \times (3 \times 5)))} := \frac{(20 \times ((1^6) \times 9))}{(7 \times ((8 + (4 \times 3)) \times 5))} := \frac{(201 + 69)}{(78 + (4 \times (3^5)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20196}{43758} &:= \frac{(((2 \times (0 - 1)) + 9) \times 6)}{((4^3) + ((7 \times 5) - 8))} := \frac{((2 - (0 - 1)) \times 96)}{((43 + (7 \times 5)) \times 8)} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + (1 \times 9))) + 6)}{(4 - (3 + (7 - 58)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + (0 - 1)) \times (9 \times 6))}{(4 + ((3 \times (7 \times 5)) + 8))} := \frac{((20 - (1^9)) \times 6)}{(((4 \times 3) + 7) \times (5 + 8))} := \frac{((20 + (1 + 9)) \times 6)}{(((4^3) \times 7) - 58)} \\
 &:= \frac{((201 - 9) \times 6)}{(4 \times ((3 + 75) \times 8))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (1 + (9 + 6))))}{(43 - (7 + (5 - 8)))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (1 + (9 - 6))))}{(4 + (3 - (7 - (5 + 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((0 \times 19) + 6))}{((4 \times (3 \times 7)) - 58)} := \frac{(2 \times (0 - ((1 - 9) \times 6)))}{((4 \times ((3 + 7) \times 5)) + 8)} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + ((1 + 9) \times 6)))}{(4 - ((3 - (7 \times 5)) \times 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (1 \times (9 + 6))))}{(4 + ((3 \times 7) + (5 \times 8)))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (1 \times 96)))}{(((4^3) - (7 + 5)) \times 8)} := \frac{(20 \times (1 \times (9 + 6)))}{((43 + 7) \times (5 + 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(20 \times (1 \times 96))}{((4^3) \times (7 + 58))} := \frac{(20 + (1 + (9 + 6)))}{(((4 + (3 + 7)) \times 5) + 8)} := \frac{(20 + 196)}{((43 - 7) \times (5 + 8))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{21735}{49680} &:= \frac{((2 \times ((1 + 7)^3) + 5)}{(49 \times (6 \times (8 - 0)))} := \frac{((2 + (1^7)) \times 35)}{(((4 \times 9) - 6) \times (8 - 0))} := \frac{((2 + (1 + (7 - 3))) \times 5)}{((4 - (9 - 6)) \times 80)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + 17) \times 35)}{((4 + (9 + 6)) \times 80)} := \frac{((21 + 7) \times (3 + 5))}{((4^9 - 6) \times (8 - 0))} := \frac{(2 \times (1 \times (7 \times (3 \times 5))))}{(4 \times ((9 + 6) \times (8 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (1 \times 735))}{(((4 \times 9) + 6) \times 80)} := \frac{(2 \times (1 + ((7 - 3) \times 5)))}{(4 \times ((9 - 6) \times (8 - 0)))} := \frac{(2 + ((1^7) \times (3^5)))}{((4 + (9 - 6)) \times 80)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (1 \times ((7 \times 3) + 5)))}{(4 \times (96 - 80))} := \frac{(2 + (1 \times ((7^3) + 5)))}{((4 + 96) \times (8 - 0))} := \frac{(2 + (1 \times (7 + (3^5))))}{(496 + 80)} \\
 &:= \frac{(21 \times ((7 + 3) \times 5))}{(((4 \times 9) - 6) \times 80)} := \frac{(21 \times ((7 - 3) \times 5))}{(4 \times ((9 - 6) \times 80))} := \frac{(21 + ((7^3) \times 5))}{(496 \times (8 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(21 + (7 + 35))}{((4^9 - 6) + 80)} := \frac{(21 + 735)}{(4 \times (9 \times (6 \times (8 - 0))))} := \frac{(217 - 35)}{(4 \times (96 + (8 - 0)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{28710}{45936} &:= \frac{(((2 \times 8)^7) \times 10)}{(4 \times ((5 + (9 \times 3))^6))} := \frac{(((2 \times 8) + 7) \times 10)}{(4 \times (5 + (93 - 6)))} := \frac{(((2^8)^7) \times 10)}{((4^5)^{9+3-6})} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (8 + 7)) + 10)}{(4 + (5 \times (9 - (3 - 6))))} := \frac{((2 + (8 + 7)) \times 10)}{(4 \times (59 + (3 + 6)))} := \frac{((2 + 8) \times (7 - (1 - 0)))}{(4 + (5 + (93 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((28 \times 7) - (1 - 0))}{((4 + ((5 \times 9) + 3)) \times 6)} := \frac{(2 - (8 - (71 - 0)))}{(4 \times (5 + ((9 \times 3) - 6)))} := \frac{(2 \times ((8 - 7) \times 10))}{(4 - (5 - ((9 \times 3) + 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 + ((5 \times 9) + 3)) \times 6)}{(2 \times (8 + (7 \times (1 - 0))))} := \frac{(2 \times (8 + (7 + 10)))}{(2 \times (8 + (7 - 10)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times ((5 - 9) \times (3 - 6)))}{(2 + (8 + (7 \times 10)))} := \frac{(4 - (5 - (9 \times (3 + 6))))}{(2 + (8 + 710))} := \frac{(4 + ((5 - 9) \times (3 - 6)))}{(2 + (87 + (1 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (5 - (9 - 36)))}{(4 \times ((5 \times 9) + 3) \times 6)} := \frac{(4 \times ((5 \times 9) + 3) \times 6)}{(4 \times ((5 \times 9) + 3) \times 6)} := \frac{(4 \times ((5 \times 9) + 3) \times 6)}{(4 \times ((5 \times 9) + 3) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(28 + (7 \times (1 - 0)))}{(4 \times (5 - (9 - (3 \times 6))))} := \frac{(28 + (7 + 10))}{(4 + (59 + (3 + 6)))} := \frac{(28 + (7 - 10))}{(4 + ((5 \times 9) + 3) \times 6)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{29835}{71604} &:= \frac{(((2 + 9) \times 8) + 3) \times 5}{(7 \times (160 - 4))} := \frac{(((2 + 9) \times (8 - 3)) + 5)}{((7 - 1) \times (6 \times (0 + 4)))} := \frac{((2 \times (9 + (8 + 3))) + 5)}{((7 \times (16 - 0)) - 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (9 + (8 + 3))) - 5)}{(7 \times (16 + (0 - 4)))} := \frac{((2^9 - 8 + 3) \times 5)}{((7 + 1) \times (6 \times (0 + 4)))} := \frac{((2^9) + (83 + 5))}{((7 - 1) \times (60 \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + ((9 - 8) \times 3)) \times 5)}{((7 - 1) \times (6 - (0 - 4)))} := \frac{((2 + ((9 - 8)^3)) \times 5)}{((7 - 16) \times (0 - 4))} := \frac{((2 + (9 + (8 + 3))) \times 5)}{((7 - (1 - 60)) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + 98) \times (3 + 5))}{((7 + 1) \times (60 \times 4))} := \frac{(2 - (9 + (8 - 35)))}{((7 - (1 - (6 - 0))) \times 4)} := \frac{(2 \times ((9 \times 8) + (3 + 5)))}{((7 - 1) \times (60 + 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 + 1) \times (60 \times 4))}{(2 \times ((9 + (8 - 3)) \times 5))} := \frac{(2 \times ((9 - 8) \times 35))}{(2 \times ((9 - 8) \times 35))} := \frac{(2 \times (9 + (8 + (3 - 5))))}{(2 \times (9 + (8 + (3 - 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 - 1) \times (60 - 4))}{(2 + ((9 - 8) \times (3 + 5)))} := \frac{(7 \times (1 \times (6 \times (0 + 4))))}{(2 + (9 - (8 + (3 - 5))))} := \frac{(7 + (1 + (60 + 4)))}{(298 - (3 - 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 - (1^6 + 0)) \times 4}{((7 - (1 - (6 - (0 \times 4))))} := \frac{(7 - (1 - (6 - (0 \times 4))))}{(716 - (0 - 4))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30168}{94275} &:= \frac{((3 - (0 - (1^6))) \times 8)}{(9 + ((4^2) + 75))} := \frac{((3 - (0 - (1 + 6))) \times 8)}{((9 \times 4) + (2 \times 7)) \times 5} := \frac{((3 - (0 - (1 + 6)))^8)}{((9 \times 4) + (2 \times 7))^5} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (0 \times 16)) + 8)}{(9 + (4 \times (2^7 - 5)))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 + 16)) - 8)}{((9 \times (4 - 2)) + 7) \times 5} := \frac{((3^{-01+6}) \times 8)}{((9^4 - 2) \times 75)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 + (0 - (1 - 6))) \times 8)}{((9 + (4 + 27)) \times 5)} := \frac{((3 + (0 - 1)) \times (6 \times 8))}{((9 + (4^2)) \times (7 + 5))} := \frac{((3 + (0 - 1)) \times 68)}{((94 - (2 + 7)) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((30 - (1 - 6)) \times 8)}{((9 + (4^2)) \times (7 \times 5))} := \frac{((30 + (1 - 6)) \times 8)}{((9 + (4^2))^{7-5})} := \frac{((30 - 16) \times 8)}{((9 - 4) \times (2 \times (7 \times 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (0 - (1 + 68)))}{((9 + (4 \times (2 + 7))) \times 5)} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + ((1 + 6) \times 8)))}{((9 - (4 - 2)) \times 75)} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (16 - 8)))}{(9 - (4 - (2 \times (7 \times 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + 168))}{(9 \times ((42 - 7) \times 5))} := \frac{(3 + (0 - (1 - (6 + 8))))}{(9 + (4 + (2 + (7 \times 5))))} := \frac{(30 \times (16 - 8))}{((9 - 4) \times (2 \times 75))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{35820}{96714} &:= \frac{((3 - (5 - 8)) \times 20)}{(9 \times (6 \times (7 - (1^4))))} := \frac{((3 \times (5 \times 8)) + 20)}{(9 \times (6 \times (7 \times (1^4))))} := \frac{((3 \times (5 \times 8)) - 20)}{(9 \times (6 + ((7 - 1) \times 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3^5) \times (8 \times 20))}{(((9 - 6) \times (7 - 1))^4)} := \frac{((3^5) \times (8 + (2 - 0)))}{(9^{6-7+1+4})} := \frac{((35 \times 8) + 20)}{(96 + 714)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (5 - (82 - 0)))}{(9 \times (6 \times (7 + (1 - 4))))} := \frac{(3 - (5 + (8 - 20)))}{(9 + (6 + (7 + (1 + 4))))} := \frac{(3 \times ((5 \times 8) - 20))}{(9 \times (6 + (7 + (1 + 4))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (5 \times (8 - (2 - 0))))}{(3 \times (5 \times (8 \times (2 - 0))))} := \frac{(9 \times (6 + (7 + 14)))}{(9 \times (6 \times (7 + (1 + 4))))} := \frac{(9 \times (6 + 714))}{(3 \times (5 \times (8 \times 20)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 \times (6 + (7 + 14)))}{(3 \times (5 \times (8 + 20)))} := \frac{(9 \times (6 \times (7 + (1 + 4))))}{(3 \times (5 \times (8 + 20)))} := \frac{(9 \times (6 + 714))}{(3 + (5 - (8 - 20)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 \times ((6 \times 7) - (1 - 4)))}{(35 \times (8 - (2 - 0)))} := \frac{(9 \times (6 \times (7 + 14)))}{(35 \times (8 \times (2 - 0)))} := \frac{(9 + ((6 \times 7) - (1 - 4)))}{(358 + (2 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 \times (67 - (1 \times 4)))}{(9 \times (6 \times (7 \times (1 \times 4))))} := \frac{(9 \times (6 \times (7 \times (1 \times 4))))}{(9 \times (6 \times (7 \times (1 \times 4))))} := \frac{(967 + (1 + 4))}{(967 + (1 + 4))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{38925}{46710} &:= \frac{(((3 \times 8) - 9)^2 + 5)}{(46 \times (7 - (1 - 0)))} := \frac{((3 - ((8 - 9) \times 2)) \times 5)}{((4 + (6 - 7)) \times 10)} := \frac{((3 \times ((8 \times 9) - 2)) + 5)}{((4 \times 67) - 10)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (8 + (9 - 2))) + 5)}{((4 + 6) \times (7 - (1 - 0)))} := \frac{((3 \times (8 + (9 - 2))) - 5)}{(4 \times (6 + (7 - (1 - 0))))} := \frac{((3 \times 89) - (2 + 5))}{((46 \times 7) - 10)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 + (8 + 9)) \times (2 + 5))}{(4 \times (6 \times (7 \times (1 - 0))))} := \frac{(3 - ((8 - 9) \times (2^5)))}{((4 \times (6 + 7)) - 10)} := \frac{(3 - (8 - (9 \times 25)))}{(4 \times (67 - (1 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times ((8 - (9 - 2)) \times 5))}{(4 + (6 + (7 + (1 - 0))))} := \frac{(3 \times ((8 \times 9) - (2^5)))}{(4 \times (6 \times (7 - (1 - 0))))} := \frac{(3 \times ((8 + (9 \times 2)) \times 5))}{(467 + (1 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (8 + (9 - (2 + 5))))}{(4 \times (6 - (7 - 10)))} := \frac{(3 \times (8 + (9 - (2 - 5))))}{(4 + (67 + (1 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 + (8 - (9 + (2 - 5))))}{(4 - (6 - (7 + (1 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (8 + (9 - (2 \times 5))))}{(4 \times (6 + (7 - 10)))} := \frac{(3 + (8 + (9 + 25)))}{(46 + (7 + (1 - 0)))} := \frac{(38 \times (9 \times (2 \times 5)))}{((4^6) + (7 + (1 - 0)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{45792}{80136} &:= \frac{(((4 - (5 - 7)) \times 9)^2)}{((8 + (0 - 1)) \times (3^6))} := \frac{(((4 \times 5) - (7 + 9)) \times 2)}{(8 - ((0 \times 13) - 6))} := \frac{((4 - ((5 - 7) \times 9)) \times 2)}{(80 + (1 \times (3 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times (5 + (7 - 9)))^2)}{((8 + (0 - 1)) \times 36)} := \frac{((4 \times 57) + 92)}{(80 \times (13 - 6))} := \frac{((4 + (5 + 7)) \times (9 \times 2))}{((80 + (1 + 3)) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - ((5 \times (7 - 9)) + 2))}{(((8 - (0 - 1)) \times 3) - 6)} := \frac{(4 - ((5 \times (7 - 9)) - 2))}{((8 \times (0 - 1)) + 36)} := \frac{(4 - ((5 - 7) \times (9 \times 2)))}{((8^{-0+3}) + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (5 - (7 \times (9 - 2))))}{(80 + (1 - (3 - 6)))} := \frac{(4 - (5 \times (7 - (9 + 2))))}{((8 + (0 - (1^3))) \times 6)} := \frac{(4 - (5 \times (7 - (9 - 2))))}{(8 + (0 - (1^{36})))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times ((5 - (7 - 9)) \times 2))}{((8 \times (0 + 13)) - 6)} := \frac{(4 \times (5 - (7 - (9 + 2))))}{((8 + (0 - 1)) \times (3 + 6))} := \frac{(4 \times (5 + ((7 \times 9) - 2)))}{((80 - (1 \times 3)) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + ((5 \times 7) - (9 - 2)))}{(8 \times (0 + (13 - 6)))} := \frac{(4 + (57 + (9 + 2)))}{((8 - (0 - 13)) \times 6)} := \frac{(457 + (9 + 2))}{(801 + (3 \times 6))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{54712}{68390} &:= \frac{(((5 \times (4 + 7)) - 1) \times 2)}{((6 \times (8 \times 3)) - (9 - 0))} := \frac{(((5 \times 4) + (7 - 1))^2)}{(6 + (839 - 0))} := \frac{(((5 \times 47) - 1) \times 2)}{((68 - 3) \times (9 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 - (4 - (7 \times 1)))^2)}{(6 + (83 - (9 - 0)))} := \frac{((5 - (4 - 7)) \times 12)}{(6 \times (8 + (3 + (9 - 0))))} := \frac{((5 \times (4 + (7 - 1))) - 2)}{((6 \times 8) + (3 + (9 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 + ((4 \times 7) + 1)) \times 2)}{(6 - (8 + (3 - 90)))} := \frac{((5 + 4) \times (7 + (1^2)))}{((6 - (8 - 3)) \times 90)} := \frac{((5 + 4) \times 712)}{((6 + 83) \times 90)} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 + 47) \times (1 + 2))}{((68 \times 3) - (9 - 0))} := \frac{((5 - 4) \times (7 \times 12))}{(6 + ((8 + 3) \times (9 - 0)))} := \frac{((54 + (7 + 1)) \times 2)}{(68 - (3 - 90))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 - (4 - (7 \times (1^2))))}{(6 - (8 - (3 + (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(5 - (4 - (7 + 12)))}{(6 - (8 - (3 \times (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(5 \times (4 + (7 + (1^2))))}{((6 \times (8 + 3)) + (9 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (4 + (7 \times (1^2))))}{(6 + (8 - (3 - (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(54 \times (7 - (1^2)))}{(((6 \times 8) - 3) \times (9 - 0))} := \frac{(54 \times (7 - (1 + 2)))}{(6 \times ((8 - 3) \times (9 - 0)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{58239}{64710} &:= \frac{(((5 \times 8) - (2 \times 3)) \times 9)}{(6 + (4 \times 7)) \times 10} := \frac{(((5 \times 8) - 23) \times 9)}{((6 + (4 + 7)) \times 10)} := \frac{((5 \times 8) + 239)}{(((6 \times 4) + 7) \times 10)} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 + ((8^2) + 3)) \times 9)}{(6 + (4 + 710))} := \frac{((5 + ((8^2) - 3)) \times 9)}{(6 \times ((4 + 7) \times 10))} := \frac{((5 + (8 - (2 \times 3))) \times 9)}{(64 + (7 - (1 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 + (8 - (2 \times 3))) \times 9)}{(6 + (4 + (7 \times 10)))} := \frac{((5 + (8 - (2 - 3))) \times 9)}{((6 - 4) \times (7 \times 10))} := \frac{((5 + (8 \times (2 \times 3))) \times 9)}{((6 + 47) \times 10)} \\
 &:= \frac{((58 + (2 - 3)) \times 9)}{((64 - 7) \times 10)} := \frac{((58 - 2) \times (3 \times 9))}{(6 \times (4 \times (7 \times 10)))} := \frac{(5 \times ((8 - (2 - 3)) \times 9))}{(6 \times (4 + (71 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times ((8 + (2 \times 3)) \times 9))}{((6 + 4) \times (7 \times 10))} := \frac{(5 + (8 \times (23 + 9)))}{(6 + (4 \times (71 - 0)))} := \frac{(5 + (8 + (2 + (3 + 9))))}{(6 + (4 \times (7 - (1 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (8 + (2 + (3 - 9))))}{(6 - (4 - (7 + (1 - 0))))} := \frac{(5 + (8 + (2 + 39)))}{(6 \times (4 + (7 - (1 - 0))))} := \frac{(5 + (82 + (3 - 9)))}{((6 - (4 - 7)) \times 10)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{65432}{81790} &:= \frac{(((6 - (5 - (4 + 3)))^2)}{(8 \times ((1^7) + (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(((6 \times (5 \times (4 - 3))) + 2)}{((8 - 1) \times 7) - (9 - 0)} := \frac{(((65 - (4 + 3)) \times 2)}{((8 \times 17) + (9 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{((65 - (4 - 3)) \times 2)}{(81 + (79 - 0))} := \frac{((65 - 43) \times 2)}{((8 \times (1 + 7)) - (9 - 0))} := \frac{(6 - (5 - (4 - (3 - 2))))}{(8 - (1 - (7 - (9 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times ((5 + (4 - 3)) \times 2))}{(8 - (1 + (7 - 90)))} := \frac{(6 \times ((5 + 43) \times 2))}{(8 \times ((1^7) \times 90))} := \frac{(6 \times (5 \times (4 + 32)))}{((8 + (1 \times 7)) \times 90)} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (5 + (4 + (3^2))))}{((8 + (1 \times 7)) \times (9 - 0))} := \frac{(6 \times (5 + (4 + (3 + 2))))}{(8 + (1 \times (7 + 90)))} := \frac{(6 + ((5 + (4^3)) \times 2))}{((8 + (1 - 7)) \times 90)} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 + (5 - (4 - (3 - 2))))}{(8 - (1 \times (7 - (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(6 + (5 \times (4 + (3 \times 2))))}{(6 + (5 \times (4 + (3 \times 2))))} := \frac{(6 + (5 + (4 + (3 + 2))))}{(6 + (5 + (4 + (3 + 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 - (1 \times (7 - (9 - 0))))}{(6 + (5 + (43 - 2)))} := \frac{(8 - (1 - (7 \times (9 - 0))))}{(6 + (54 + 32))} := \frac{(8 + (1 + (7 + (9 - 0))))}{(654 - (3 \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 + (5 + (43 - 2)))}{((8 \times (1 \times 7)) + (9 - 0))} := \frac{(6 + (54 + 32))}{(8 + (17 + 90))} := \frac{(654 - (3 \times 2))}{((8 + (1^7)) \times 90)}
 \end{aligned}$$

• **Four Digit's Numerator**

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{1395}{267840} &:= \frac{(((1^3)^9) + 5)}{(2 \times (6 \times ((7 \times 8) + 40)))} := \frac{((1^3) \times (9 + 5))}{(2 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times (4 - 0)))))} := \frac{((1^3) \times (9 - 5))}{(((2^6) \times 7) + (8 \times 40))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1^3) \times 95)}{(((2^6) - 7) \times (8 \times 40))} := \frac{((1^3) + (9 - 5))}{((2 - (6 - 7)) \times (8 \times 40))} := \frac{((1 + (3 \times 9)) \times 5)}{(2 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 40))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^6) \times ((7 + 8) \times 40))}{((1 + 39) \times 5)} := \frac{((13 \times 9) - 5)}{((13 \times 9) - 5)} := \frac{((13 - 9) \times 5)}{((13 - 9) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^6) \times ((7 + 8) \times 40))}{(1 \times ((3 \times 9) + 5))} := \frac{((2^6) \times (7 \times (8 + 40)))}{(1 \times (3 \times (9 - 5)))} := \frac{((2^6) \times ((7 + 8) \times (4 - 0)))}{(1 \times (39 \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^6) \times ((7 \times 8) + 40))}{(1^{395})} := \frac{((2^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 40)))}{(1 + (3 \times (9 - 5)))} := \frac{(2 \times (6 \times (78 \times 40)))}{(2 \times (6 \times (784 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 40)))}{(1 + (39 \times 5))} := \frac{(26 \times ((7 \times 8) + 40))}{(1 + (39 - 5))} := \frac{(1 + (3 + (9 \times 5)))}{(2 \times (6 \times (784 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2^6) \times (7 \times (84 - 0))}{(2^6) \times (7 \times (84 - 0))} := \frac{(2 \times ((6 + 78) \times 40))}{(2 \times ((6 + 78) \times 40))} := \frac{(13 - (9 - 5))}{(2 \times 6)^{7-8+4+0}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{3051}{286794} &:= \frac{((3 \times (0 \times 5)) + 1)}{(2 - ((8 \times (6 \times (7 - 9))) + 4))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 + 5)) + 1)}{((2 + ((8 - 6) \times 7)) \times 94)} := \frac{((3 \times (0 + 5)) - 1)}{(2 \times ((8 + (6 - 7)) \times 94))} \\
 &:= \frac{((30 \times 5) + 1)}{(2 \times ((8 \times 67) + (9^4)))} := \frac{(3 - ((0 \times 5) - 1))}{(2 - (8 - ((6 \times (7 \times 9)) + 4)))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (5 \times 1)))}{(2 \times (8 \times ((6 \times 7) + (9 - 4))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + (8 + (6 - 7))) \times 94)}{(3 - (0 - (5 + 1)))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (5 - 1)))}{(2 - (8 - (6 + (7 \times 94))))} := \frac{(3 - (0 \times 51))}{(2 + (8 \times (6 - (7 - (9 \times 4)))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (86 \times ((7 \times 9) - 4)))}{(3^{05 \times 1})} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (5 \times 1)))}{((28 - (6 + 7)) \times 94)} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (5 + 1)))}{(2 \times ((8 - (6 - 7)) \times 94))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((2^8) - (6 + 7)) \times 94)}{(30 \times (5 \times 1))} := \frac{(3^{05-1})}{((2 + (86 - 7)) \times 94)} := \frac{(3 + ((0 \times 5) - 1))}{((2 - ((8 - (6 + 7)) \times 9)) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((8 + 67) \times 94))}{(2 \times ((8 + 67) \times 94))} := \frac{((2 \times (8 + 6)) + 7) \times 94}{((2 \times (8 + 6)) + 7) \times 94} := \frac{(30 + (5 + 1))}{((2 - (8 - (6 \times 7))) \times 94)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4653}{120978} &:= \frac{(((4 \times 6) + 5) \times 3)}{(1 \times ((20 + 9) \times 78))} := \frac{(((4 \times 6) - 5) \times 3)}{((1 - (2 \times (0 - 9))) \times 78)} := \frac{((4 - (6 - 5)) \times 3)}{((1 + (2 - (0 \times 9))) \times 78)} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 - (6 - 5))^3)}{((1^2 + 0) \times (9 \times 78))} := \frac{((4 + 6) \times (5 - 3))}{(1 \times ((2 - (0 - (9 \times 7))) \times 8))} := \frac{(4 - ((6 - 5) \times 3))}{(1 \times (2 - (0 - (9 + (7 + 8)))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - ((6 - 5)^3))}{((1^{2-0 \times 9}) \times 78)} := \frac{(4 - (6 - (5 + 3)))}{(1 \times (2 \times ((0 \times 9) + 78)))} := \frac{(4 \times (6 + (5 + 3)))}{(1 + ((209 \times 7) - 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 + (5 - 3)))}{((120 - (9 + 7)) \times 8)} := \frac{(4^{(6-5)^3})}{(1 - (2 + (0 - (97 + 8))))} := \frac{(4 + ((6 - 5) \times 3))}{(1 + ((20 \times 9) - (7 - 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + ((6 - 5)^3))}{(1 \times (2 \times (0 + (9 + (7 \times 8)))))} := \frac{(4 + (6 - (5 + 3)))}{(1 - (20 - ((9 \times 7) + 8)))} := \frac{(4 + (6 - (5 - 3)))}{((1 - ((2 \times (0 - 9)) - 7)) \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (6 + (5 - 3)))}{(1 \times ((20 \times (9 + 7)) - 8))} := \frac{(4 + (6 + 53))}{((12 - (0 - 9)) \times 78)} := \frac{(46 + (5 + 3))}{(1 \times (2 \times (0 + (9 \times 78))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{5703}{182496} &:= \frac{(5 \times (7 - 0) + 3)}{(1 \times ((8^2) \times (4 + (9 + 6))))} &:= \frac{((5 \times (7 - 0)) - 3)}{(1 \times (8 \times (2 \times (4^{9-6}))))} &:= \frac{((5 + (7 - 0)) \times 3)}{(1 \times (((8 \times 2) - 4) \times 96))} \\ &:= \frac{((5 - 7) \times (0 - 3))}{(1 \times (8 - (2 \times (4 - 96))))} &:= \frac{(5 - (7 \times (0 \times 3)))}{(1 \times (8 \times ((2 \times (4 + 9)) - 6)))} &:= \frac{(5 - (7 \times (0 - 3)))}{(1 \times (8 \times ((2 \times 49) + 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 - (7 + (0 - 3)))}{(1 \times (8 + (2 \times (4 \times (9 - 6)))))} &:= \frac{(5 \times (7 - (0 - 3)))}{(1 \times (8 \times (2 \times (4 + 96))))} &:= \frac{(5 \times (7 + (0 - 3)))}{(1 \times (8 \times (2 + ((4 + 9) \times 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + (7 - (0 \times 3)))}{(1 \times (8 \times ((2^4) \times (9 - 6))))} &:= \frac{(5 + (7 - (0 - 3)))}{(1 \times (8 \times (2 + (4 + (9 \times 6)))))} &:= \frac{(5 + (7 + (0 - 3)))}{(1 \times ((8 \times 24) + 96))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + (70 + 3))}{((18 + (2 \times 4)) \times 96)} &:= \frac{(5 + (70 - 3))}{(1 \times ((8 + (2^4)) \times 96))} &:= \frac{(57 - (0 \times 3))}{(1 \times (8 \times ((2 + (4 \times 9)) \times 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(57 - (0 - 3))}{(1 \times (8 \times ((2^4) \times (9 + 6))))} &:= \frac{(57 \times (0 + 3))}{(1824 \times (9 - 6))} &:= \frac{(57 + (0 - 3))}{(1 \times ((8 + 24) \times (9 \times 6)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{6352}{107984} &:= \frac{(((6 - 3) \times 5) + 2)}{((1^{07}) + (9 \times (8 \times 4)))} &:= \frac{((6^3) + (5^2))}{(1 - (0 - ((7 + (9 - 8))^4)))} &:= \frac{((6 + (3 \times 5)) \times 2)}{(1 \times (0 + (7 \times (98 + 4))))} \\ &:= \frac{((6 + (3 - 5)) \times 2)}{((10 + (7 + (9 + 8))) \times 4)} &:= \frac{((6 - 3) \times (5 \times 2))}{(10 + ((7 \times (9 \times 8)) - 4))} &:= \frac{((6 - 3) \times (5 + 2))}{((10 + 7) \times (9 + (8 + 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - (3 - (5 \times 2)))}{(1 - (0 - (((7 \times 9) - 8) \times 4)))} &:= \frac{(6 - (3 - (5^2)))}{(1 \times (0 + (7 \times ((9 + 8) \times 4))))} &:= \frac{(6 - (3 - (5 - 2)))}{(1 + (0 - (7 - (9 \times (8 + 4)))))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times ((3 \times 5) + 2))}{((10 + 7) \times (98 + 4))} &:= \frac{(6 \times (3 + (5 - 2)))}{((10 + 7) \times (9 \times (8 - 4)))} &:= \frac{(6 \times (35 \times 2))}{(10 \times (7 \times (98 + 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + ((3 + 5) \times 2))}{(10 - ((7 - 98) \times 4))} &:= \frac{(6 + (3 - (5 + 2)))}{(1 \times (0 - (7 - (9 + (8 \times 4)))))} &:= \frac{(6 + (3 \times 52))}{(10 + (7 \times (98 \times 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + (3 + (5 - 2)))}{((1 - (0 - (7 + 9))) \times (8 + 4))} &:= \frac{(6 + (35 \times 2))}{((10 + 7) \times ((9 \times 8) + 4))} &:= \frac{(63 - (5^2))}{(10 + ((79 \times 8) + 4))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{7029}{154638} &:= \frac{((7 - (0 - 2)) \times 9)}{(1 \times (54 + ((6^3) \times 8)))} &:= \frac{((7 \times (0 \times 2)) + 9)}{(1 \times (54 + (6 \times (3 \times 8))))} &:= \frac{((7 \times (0 + 2)) + 9)}{(1 + (5 - (4 - (63 \times 8))))} \\ &:= \frac{((7 \times (0 + 2)) - 9)}{(1 \times (5 \times (4 - (6 - (3 \times 8)))))} &:= \frac{((7^{02}) + 9)}{((1 + (5 - 4)) \times 638)} &:= \frac{((7^{02}) - 9)}{(1 \times (5 \times (4 \times (6 + 38))))} \\ &:= \frac{((70 + 2) \times 9)}{(((1 + 5)^4) \times (6 - (3 - 8)))} &:= \frac{(7 - ((0 \times 2) - 9))}{(1 \times ((5 \times (4 \times (6 \times 3))) - 8))} &:= \frac{(7 - (0 - (2 \times 9)))}{(1 \times (5 \times ((4 + 6) \times (3 + 8))))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 - (0 - (2 + 9)))}{(1 \times ((5 + 4) \times (6 + 38)))} &:= \frac{(7 - (0 \times 29))}{(1 + (5 + (4 + (6 \times (3 \times 8)))))} &:= \frac{(7 - (0 - 29))}{(154 + 638)} \\ &:= \frac{(7 \times ((0 \times 2) + 9))}{((1 + (5 \times 4)) \times (6 \times (3 + 8)))} &:= \frac{(7 \times (0 + (2 + 9)))}{(154 \times (6 - (3 - 8)))} &:= \frac{(70 - (2 \times 9))}{(1 \times ((5 + (46 \times 3)) \times 8))} \\ &:= \frac{(70 \times (2 \times 9))}{((1 + 54) \times (63 \times 8))} &:= \frac{(70 + (2 \times 9))}{(1 \times (((5 + 4) \times (6^3)) - 8))} &:= \frac{(70 - 29)}{(1 + (5 + (4 \times ((6^3) + 8))))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7956}{103428} & := \frac{(((7+9) \times 5) - 6)}{(10 + (34 \times 28))} & := \frac{((7 \times (9+5)) + 6)}{(((1 - (0 - (3 \times 4)))^2) \times 8)} & := \frac{((7 \times (9-5)) + 6)}{((10 \times (3+42)) - 8)} \\
 & := \frac{((7 \times (9-5)) - 6)}{(((10-3) \times 42) - 8)} & := \frac{((7 \times 9) - (5 \times 6))}{((10^3) + 428)} & := \frac{((7 \times 9) - (5-6))}{((103 \times (4 \times 2)) + 8)} \\
 & := \frac{((7 \times 9) - 56)}{((7 \times 9) - 56)} & := \frac{((7-9) \times (5-6))}{((1 \times (0 + ((3^4) + (2+8))))} & := \frac{(7 - (9 - (5 \times 6)))}{((1 - (0 - (3 \times 4))) \times 28)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((3^4) + (2+8))))}{(7 - (9 - (5 + 6)))} & := \frac{(7 - (9 \times (5 - 6)))}{(7 - (9 \times (5 - 6)))} & := \frac{(7 \times (9 - (5 - 6)))}{(7 \times (9 - (5 - 6)))} \\
 & := \frac{(103 + (4 + (2 + 8)))}{(7 \times (9 + (5 + 6)))} & := \frac{((1 - (0 - (3 \times 4))) \times (2 \times 8))}{(7 \times (9 + (5 - 6)))} & := \frac{(10 \times ((3^4) + (2 + 8)))}{(7 + (9 - (5 + 6)))} \\
 & := \frac{((10-3) \times (4 + (2^8)))}{(7 + (9 + (5 + 6)))} & := \frac{(((10 \times 3) - 4) \times 28)}{(7 + (9 + 56))} & := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((3^4) - (2 \times 8))))}{(79 - (5 - 6))} \\
 & := \frac{(7 + (9 + (5 + 6)))}{(1 - (0 - (342 + 8)))} & := \frac{((10^3) - (4 \times (2 \times 8)))}{((1 - (0 - 3)) \times (4 + (2^8)))} & := \frac{(79 - (5 - 6))}{((1 - (0 - 3)) \times (4 + (2^8)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.18 19 Equivalent Blocks

• Five Digit's Numerator

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10476}{39285} & := \frac{(((1^{04}) + 7) \times 6)}{(3 + (92 + 85))} & := \frac{(((10+4) \times 7) - 6)}{(3 - (9 \times (2 - (8 \times 5))))} & := \frac{(((10-4) \times 7) - 6)}{(3 \times (9 \times (2 + (8 - 5))))} & := \frac{((1^{04}) \times 76)}{((3 - (9 \times (2 - 8))) \times 5)} \\
 & := \frac{(((1 + (0 - (4 - 7))) \times 6)}{((3 + (9 - (2 - 8))) \times 5)} & := \frac{(((1 + (0 - (4 - 7)))^6)}{((3 + 9) \times ((2^8) \times 5))} & := \frac{((10 \times (4 + 7)) + 6)}{((3 + (92 - 8)) \times 5)} & := \frac{((10 \times (4 + 7)) - 6)}{(3 \times (((9 \times 2) + 8) \times 5))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (4 \times (7 + 6))))}{(39 \times (2 + (8 - 5)))} & := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (4 \times (7 - 6))))}{(3 - (9 - ((2 \times 8) + 5)))} & := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (4 + 76)))}{(3 + (9 \times (28 + 5)))} & := \frac{(1 \times (0 + 476))}{(3 \times ((9 - 2) \times 85))} \\
 & := \frac{(10 - ((4 - 7) \times 6))}{(3 \times (9 + (2 \times (8 + 5))))} & := \frac{(10 \times ((4 \times 7) + 6))}{((3 + (9 \times 28)) \times 5)} & := \frac{(10 \times (4 \times (7 + 6)))}{(39 \times ((2 + 8) \times 5))} & := \frac{(10 \times (4 \times (7 - 6)))}{(3 \times (((9 \times 2) - 8) \times 5))} \\
 & := \frac{(10 + ((4 \times 7) + 6))}{((39 + (2 - 8)) \times 5)} & := \frac{(10 + (4 + (7 \times 6)))}{(3 + (9 \times (28 - 5)))} & := \frac{(10 + (47 \times 6))}{(3 \times (((9^2) - 8) \times 5))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13527}{48096} & := \frac{(((1 + (3 + 5)) \times 2)^7)}{(((4 - 8) \times (0 - 9))^6)} & := \frac{(((1 + 3)^5) \times (2 + 7))}{((4 \times (8 - 0))^{9-6})} & := \frac{(((13 + 5)^2) \times 7)}{((4 + 80) \times 96)} & := \frac{((1 - (3 - 5)) \times 27)}{(48 \times ((0 \times 9) + 6))} \\
 & := \frac{(((1 + (3 + 5)) \times (2^7))}{4^{8 \times 0 \times 9 \times 6}} & := \frac{((1 + 35) \times (2 + 7))}{((4 + (8 - 0)) \times 96)} & := \frac{((13 + 5) \times 27)}{(4 \times (8 \times (0 + (9 \times 6))))} & := \frac{(1 \times ((3 \times (5 - 2))^7))}{(4 \times (8 \times (0 + (9^6))))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times ((3^5) \times (2^7)))}{(48^{09-6})} & := \frac{(1 \times ((3^5) + 27))}{(4 \times (80 \times (9 - 6)))} & := \frac{(1 \times (3 \times ((5 \times 2) - 7)))}{(4 \times (8 - (0 \times 96)))} & := \frac{(1 \times (3 \times ((5^2) - 7)))}{(4 \times (8 \times ((0 \times 9) + 6)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (3 \times (5 \times (2 + 7))))}{(4 \times (8 \times (0 + (9 + 6))))} & := \frac{(1 \times (3 \times (5 \times 27)))}{(480 \times (9 - 6))} & := \frac{(1 \times (3^{5 \times 2 - 7}))}{(4 \times (8 \times (0 + (9 - 6))))} & := \frac{(1 + (3 + (5 + 27)))}{((4 \times (8 - 0)) + 96)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (3 + (52 + 7)))}{((4 \times 80) - 96)} & := \frac{135 + 27}{480 + 96} & := \frac{135 - 27}{480 - 96} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13584}{67920} & := \frac{(((1 + (3 + 5)) \times 8) + 4)}{((6 \times (7 \times 9)) + (2 - 0))} & := \frac{((1^3) \times (5 + (8 + 4)))}{(67 + (9 \times (2 - 0)))} & := \frac{((13 + 5) \times 84)}{(6 \times (7 \times (9 \times 20)))} & := \frac{(1 - (3 - ((5 \times 8) - 4)))}{((6 + 79) \times (2 - 0))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (3 - (5 + (8 - 4))))}{((6 \times 7) - (9 - (2 - 0)))} & := \frac{(1 \times ((35 \times 8) - 4))}{((6 + (7 \times 9)) \times 20)} & := \frac{(1 \times (3 - (5 - (8 \times 4))))}{(6 \times (7 + (9 \times (2 - 0))))} & := \frac{(1 \times (3 - (5 - (8 - 4))))}{(6 - (7 + (9 - 20)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (3 \times ((5 \times 8) + 4)))}{(((6 \times 7) - 9) \times 20)} & := \frac{(1 \times (3 + (5 \times (8 - 4))))}{(((6 + 7) \times 9) - (2 - 0))} & := \frac{(1 \times (3 + (5 + (8 - 4))))}{(67 - (9 - (2 - 0)))} & := \frac{(1 + ((3^5) - (8 + 4)))}{((67 - 9) \times 20)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (3 - ((5 - 8) \times 4)))}{(6 - (7 - (9^2 + 0)))} & := \frac{(1 + (3 - (5 - (8 + 4))))}{(6 + (7 \times (9 - (2 - 0))))} & := \frac{(1 + (3^{5-8+4}))}{(6 + (7 + (9 - (2 - 0))))} & := \frac{(1 + (3 + (5 + (8 + 4))))}{(6 + (7 + (92 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (3 + (5 + (8 - 4))))}{(6 + (79 - 20))} & := \frac{(1 + (35 - (8 - 4)))}{((6 - (7 - 9)) \times 20)} & := \frac{(13 \times ((5 \times 8) - 4))}{((6 + 7) \times (9 \times 20))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{17254}{60389} &:= \frac{(((1^{72}) + 5) \times 4)}{(6 \times (0 - (3 - (8 + 9))))} := \frac{(((1^{72}) + 5)^4)}{((60 + 3) \times (8 \times 9))} := \frac{(((1 + 7)^2) \times (5 + 4))}{(((6^{03}) + 8) \times 9)} := \frac{((1 + (7 + (2 \times 5))) \times 4)}{((60 \times 3) + (8 \times 9))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (7 - (2 + (5 \times 4))))}{(60 - (3 - (8 - 9)))} := \frac{(1 \times (((7^2) + 5) \times 4))}{((60 + (3 \times 8)) \times 9)} := \frac{(1 \times (7 \times ((2^5) + 4)))}{((60 + 38) \times 9)} := \frac{(1 \times (7 \times (2 \times (5 + 4))))}{((60 - (3 + 8)) \times 9)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (7 + (2 + (5 + 4))))}{(((6 - (0 - 3)) \times 8) - 9)} := \frac{(1 \times (7 + (25 + 4)))}{((6 - ((0 \times 3) - 8)) \times 9)} := \frac{(1 \times (7 + (25 - 4)))}{(6 - (0 - (3 + 89)))} := \frac{(1 + ((7 \times 25) - 4))}{(603 + (8 - 9))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (7 - ((2 \times 5) - 4)))}{(6 + ((0 \times 3) - (8 - 9)))} := \frac{(1 + (7 - (2 \times (5 - 4))))}{((6 \times (0 - (3 - 8))) - 9)} := \frac{(1 + (7 \times (2 + (5 + 4))))}{(6 - (0 - (3 \times 89)))} := \frac{(1 + (7 + (2 \times (5 + 4))))}{((60 \times 3) - 89)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (7 + (2 \times (5 - 4))))}{(1 + (7 - (0 - (38 - 9))))} := \frac{(1 + (7 + (2 + (5 \times 4))))}{(6 - (0 - ((3 + 8) \times 9)))} := \frac{(17 \times (2 \times (5 + 4)))}{((60 + 3) \times (8 + 9))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{19708}{24635} &:= \frac{(((1 + 9)^7 + 0) \times 8)}{(((2^4) - 6)^{3+5})} := \frac{((1 - (9 + 7)) \times (0 - 8))}{(((2^4) - 6) \times (3 \times 5))} := \frac{((1^9) \times (70 \times 8))}{((2 + (46 \times 3)) \times 5)} := \frac{((1 + (9 \times (7 - 0))) \times 8)}{(2 \times ((4^6 - 3) \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{((19 - (7 - 0)) \times 8)}{(2 \times (4 \times ((6 - 3) \times 5)))} := \frac{(1 - (9 + (7 \times (0 - 8))))}{((2 - (4 - 6)) \times (3 \times 5))} := \frac{(1 \times ((9 - (7 - 0))^8))}{(((2 - (4 - 6))^3) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 \times ((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 8))}{(2 \times ((4 + 6) \times (3 + 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (9 \times (7 \times (0 + 8))))}{((24 - 6) \times 35)} := \frac{(1 \times (9 + (7 - (0 \times 8))))}{(2 + (4 + (6 + (3 + 5))))} := \frac{(1 \times (9 + (7 - (0 - 8))))}{((24 - (6 \times 3)) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 \times (9 + (7 + (0 - 8))))}{(2 + (4 + (6 + (3 - 5))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + ((9 \times (7 - 0)) - 8))}{(2 \times ((4 + (6 - 3)) \times 5))} := \frac{(1 + (9 \times (7 - (0 \times 8))))}{((2 - (4 - (6 \times 3))) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 + (9 \times (7 - (0 - 8))))}{(((2^4) + (6 \times 3)) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 + (9 + (70 - 8)))}{(2 \times (4 + (6 + 35)))} \\ &:= \frac{(19 - (7 - (0 \times 8)))}{(2 + (4 - (6 - (3 \times 5))))} := \frac{(19 - (7 - (0 - 8)))}{((2 - (4 - (6 - 3))) \times 5)} := \frac{(19 - (7 + (0 - 8)))}{((2^4) - (6 - (3 \times 5)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{27458}{96103} &:= \frac{((2 \times ((7 \times 4) - 5)) + 8)}{(9 + (6 \times (10 \times 3)))} := \frac{((2 \times (7 - (4 - 5))) + 8)}{((9 \times 6) + (10 \times 3))} := \frac{((2 \times (7 + (4 - 5))) + 8)}{(9 + (61 - (0 \times 3)))} := \frac{((2 \times 7) + ((4 \times 5) + 8))}{((9 \times (6 + 10)) + 3)} \\ &:= \frac{((2 \times 7) + ((4 - 5) \times 8))}{(9 - (6 \times (1 + (0 - 3))))} := \frac{((2 \times 74) - (5 \times 8))}{(9 \times (6 \times (10 - 3)))} := \frac{((2^7) + ((4 \times 5) + 8))}{((9 \times (61 - 0)) - 3)} := \frac{((2 + (7 - 4)) \times 58)}{(9 + (6 + (10^3)))} \\ &:= \frac{((2 - 7) \times (4 \times (5 - 8)))}{((9 + (61 - 0)) \times 3)} := \frac{(2 - (7 - (4 - (5 - 8))))}{(9 - (6 - (1 - (0 - 3))))} := \frac{(2 - (7 + (4 - (5 + 8))))}{(9 + (6 - (1^03)))} := \frac{(2 \times (7 - ((4 - 5) \times 8)))}{((9 + 6) \times (10 - 3))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (7 - (4 + (5 - 8))))}{((9 + (6 - (1 - 0))) \times 3)} := \frac{(2 \times (7 + (4 - (5 - 8))))}{(96 - (1 + (0 - 3)))} := \frac{(2 + ((7 - 4) \times 58))}{(9 + (610 - 3))} := \frac{(2 + (7 - (4 - (5 + 8))))}{(9 \times (6 + (1^03)))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (7 - (4 + (5 - 8))))}{(9 + (6 + (10 + 3)))} := \frac{(2 + (7 + (4 - (5 - 8))))}{((9 \times 6) - (1 + (0 - 3)))} := \frac{(2 + (74 - (5 \times 8)))}{(96 + (10 \times 3))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{56984}{71230} &:= \frac{(((5 \times 6) - 9) \times (8 - 4))}{(7 \times (12 + (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(((5 - ((6 - 9) \times 8)) \times 4)}{((71 \times 2) + (3 - 0))} := \frac{(((5 - (6 - (9 \times 8))) \times 4)}{(71 \times (2 + (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(((5 - (6 - 9)) \times (8 + 4))}{((7 - (1 + 2)) \times 30)} \\ &:= \frac{(((5 + (6 + 9)) \times (8 + 4))}{((7 + (1 + 2)) \times 30)} := \frac{(((5 + (6 - 9)) \times 84)}{(7 \times ((1^2) \times 30))} := \frac{(5 - (6 - (9 - (8 - 4))))}{(7 - (1 - (2 - (3 - 0))))} := \frac{(5 - (6 - (9 + (8 + 4))))}{(7 - (12 - 30))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 - (6 - (9 + (8 - 4))))}{(5 - (6 - (9 + (8 - 4))))} := \frac{(5 \times ((6 - (9 - 8)) \times 4))}{(5 \times (6 \times ((9 - 8) \times 4)))} := \frac{(5 \times (6 \times ((9 - 8) \times 4)))}{(5 + (6 + (9 - (8 + 4))))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + (1 \times (2^3 + 0)))}{(5 + (6 + (9 + (8 \times 4))))} := \frac{((7 - (1 \times 2))^3 + 0)}{(5 + (6 + (9 + (8 + 4))))} := \frac{((7 - (1 \times 2)) \times 30)}{(5 + (6 + (9 + (8 - 4))))} := \frac{(7 + ((1^2) \times (3 - 0)))}{(5 + (6 + (9 + 84)))} \\ &:= \frac{(71 - (2 \times (3 - 0)))}{(71 - (2 \times (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(7 + (1 + (2 + 30)))}{(7 + (1 \times (23 - 0)))} := \frac{(7 + (1 \times (23 - 0)))}{(7 + (123 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{(56 \times (9 \times (8 - 4)))}{(7 \times (12 \times 30))} := \frac{(56 \times (9 + (8 + 4)))}{((7 \times (1 \times 2)) \times 30)} := \frac{(56^{(9-8)^4})}{(71 + (2 - (3 - 0)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{63528}{79410} &:= \frac{(((6 - (3 - 5))^2) \times 8)}{((7 + 9) \times (4 \times 10))} := \frac{((6 - (3 - (5 + 2))) \times 8)}{(7 + (94 - (1 - 0)))} := \frac{((6 \times (3 + (5^2))) - 8)}{((7 + (9 + 4)) \times 10)} := \frac{((6 \times (3 + (5 + 2))) + 8)}{(79 - (4 - 10))} \\ &:= \frac{((6 \times (3 + (5 + 2))) - 8)}{(79 - (4 + 10))} := \frac{((6 \times (3 + (5 - 2))) - 8)}{(7 \times (9 - (4 \times (1 - 0))))} := \frac{((6 + (3 - (5 + 2))) \times 8)}{(7 + (9 + (4 \times (1 - 0))))} := \frac{((6 + (3 - 5)) \times (2 \times 8))}{((7 + 9) \times (4 + (1 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{((6 + (35 + 2)) \times 8)}{((7 + (9 \times 4)) \times 10)} := \frac{((6 - 3) \times ((5^2) \times 8))}{((79 - 4) \times 10)} := \frac{(6 - (3 - (5 + 28)))}{((7 \times (9 - 4)) + 10)} := \frac{(6 - (3 \times (5 \times (2 - 8))))}{((7 + (9 - 4)) \times 10)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times ((3 - 5) \times (2 - 8)))}{((7 \times (9 + 4)) - (1 - 0))} := \frac{(6 \times (3 - (5 - (2 + 8))))}{((7 \times 9) - (4 - (1 - 0)))} := \frac{(6 \times (3 - (5 + (2 - 8))))}{(7 + (9 + (4 + 10)))} := \frac{(6 \times (3 + (5 - (2 - 8))))}{(7 \times (9 - (4 - 10)))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + (3 \times ((5 \times 2) + 8)))}{(79 - (4 \times (1 - 0)))} := \frac{(6 + (3 + (5 - (2 - 8))))}{((7 \times (9 - 4)) - 10)} := \frac{(6 + (3 + (5 + (2 - 8))))}{(7 + (9 + (4 - 10)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{67352}{84190} &:= \frac{((6 \times (7 - (3 - 5))) - 2)}{(84 - (19 - 0))} := \frac{((6 \times (7 + (3 - 5))) - 2)}{(8 + ((4 - 1) \times (9 - 0)))} := \frac{((6 + (7 + 35))^2)}{(8 \times (4 \times (1 \times 90)))} := \frac{(6 - (7 - (3 + (5 \times 2))))}{((8 \times (4 - 1)) - (9 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - (7 - (35 + 2)))}{((8 - (4 - 1)) \times (9 - 0))} := \frac{(6 - (7 - (35 - 2)))}{(8 \times (4 + (1^9 + 0)))} := \frac{(6 \times ((7 + (3 - 5)) \times 2))}{(84 - (1 \times (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(6 \times ((73 + 5) \times 2))}{((8 + (4 + 1)) \times 90)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times (7 \times ((3 + 5) \times 2)))}{(84 \times (1 + (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(6 \times (7 + (3 \times (5 - 2))))}{((8 + 4) \times (1 + (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(6 \times (73 - (5^2)))}{((8 - (4 \times 1)) \times 90)} := \frac{(6^{7+3-5-2})}{((8 - (4 + 1)) \times 90)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + ((7 + (3 - 5)) \times 2))}{(8 + (4 - (1 - (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(6 + ((7 + 3) \times (5^2)))}{(8 \times (4 \times (1 + (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(6 + (7 - (3 \times (5 - 2))))}{(8 - (4 - (1^9 + 0)))} := \frac{(6 + (7 \times (3 + (5 + 2))))}{(8 - (4 - (1 + 90)))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + (7 + (3 + 52)))}{(84 + (1^9 + 0))} := \frac{(6 + (73 + (5^2)))}{((8 \times (4 + 1)) + 90)} := \frac{(673 + (5 + 2))}{(841 + (9 - 0))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{71236}{89045} &:= \frac{(((7 + 1)^2) \times (3 \times 6))}{(8 \times (9 \times (0 + (4 \times 5))))} := \frac{(((7 - (1 \times (2 + 3)))^6)}{(8 \times (9 + (0 - (4 - 5))))} := \frac{((7 \times (1 \times 2)) + (3 \times 6))}{(8 \times ((9 \times (0 \times 4)) + 5))} := \frac{((7 \times (1 \times 2)) - (3 - 6))}{((8 + (9 + (0 - 4))) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{((7 \times (1 + 2)) + (3 - 6))}{((89 + (0 - 4)) \times 5)} := \frac{(((7 + (1 \times (2 + 3))) \times 6)}{(89 + (0 - (4 - 5)))} := \frac{(((7 + (1^2)) \times 36)}{(8 \times (9 \times ((0 \times 4) + 5)))} := \frac{(((7 + 1) \times (2 + 36))}{(((8 \times (9 - 0)) + 4) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{((71 \times 2) + (3 \times 6))}{(8 \times ((9 + (0 - 4)) \times 5))} := \frac{(7 - (1 + ((2^3) - 6)))}{((8 \times (9 \times (0 \times 4))) + 5)} := \frac{(7 \times ((1 - (2 - 3))^6))}{(8 \times (90 - (4 \times 5)))} := \frac{(7 \times (1 + (2 + (3 + 6))))}{((8 + (9 - (0 - 4))) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + (1 \times (2 - (3 - 6))))}{((8 - (9 + (0 - 4))) \times 5)} := \frac{(7 + (1 \times (23 + 6)))}{((8 \times (9 + (0 - 4))) + 5)} := \frac{(7 + (1 + (2 + (3 \times 6))))}{((8 \times (9 + (0 - 4))) - 5)} := \frac{(7 + (12 + (3^6)))}{(890 + 45)} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + (12 + (3 - 6)))}{((8 - 9) \times (0 - (4 \times 5)))} := \frac{(712 \times (3 + 6))}{(890 \times (4 + 5))} := \frac{(712 - 36)}{(890 - 45)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{74528}{93160} &:= \frac{(((7 \times 4) + 5) \times (2 \times 8))}{((9 + (3 - 1)) \times 60)} := \frac{(((7 - 4)^5) \times (2 \times 8))}{((9^3 - 1) \times 60)} := \frac{(((7 - ((4 - 5) \times 2)) \times 8)}{(9 \times (3 + (1 + (6 - 0))))} := \frac{(((7 - (4 - (5 + 2))) \times 8)}{(9 + (31 + 60))} \\ &:= \frac{(((7 \times (4 \times 5)) + (2 \times 8))}{(9 + (31 \times (6 - 0)))} := \frac{(((7 \times 4) + ((5 - 2) \times 8))}{(9 - (3 + (1 - 60)))} := \frac{(((7 + (4 + (5^2))) \times 8)}{((9 - (3 \times 1)) \times 60)} := \frac{(((7 + (4 - 5)) \times (2^8))}{((9 + 3) \times 160)} \\ &:= \frac{(((7 + (4 - 5)) \times (2 + 8))}{((9^3 - 1) - (6 - 0))} := \frac{(((74 - (5 + 2)) \times 8)}{((9^3) + (1 - 60))} := \frac{(((7 - 4) \times (5 \times (2 \times 8)))}{((7 - 4) \times (5 \times (2 \times 8)))} := \frac{(((7 - 4) \times (52 \times 8))}{(((9 \times 3) - 1) \times 60)} \\ &:= \frac{(((7 - 4) \times (52 + 8))}{(9 \times (31 - (6 - 0)))} := \frac{(((7 - 45) \times (2 - 8))}{((9 \times 31) + (6 - 0))} := \frac{(((7 - (4 - (5 + (2 \times 8))))}{(9 + (3 \times (1 + (6 - 0))))} := \frac{(7 - (4 + (5 + (2 - 8))))}{(9 - (3 + (1^6 + 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 \times (4 \times (5 + (2 \times 8))))}{((9^3 \times 1) + (6 - 0))} := \frac{(7 \times (4 + (52 - 8)))}{((9 - (3 - 1)) \times 60)} := \frac{(7 + (4 - (5 - (2 + 8))))}{((9 \times 3) - (1 + (6 - 0)))} \end{aligned}$$

• Four Digit's Numerator

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{8136}{274590} &:= \frac{((8 - (1 + 3)) \times 6)}{(2 \times ((7 \times 45) + 90))} &:= \frac{((8 \times (1 \times 3)) \times 6)}{(((2^7) + (4^5)) \times 90)} &:= \frac{((8 \times (1 + 3)) \times 6)}{((2 + 7) \times ((4^5) \times 90))} &:= \frac{((8 + (1 - 3)) \times 6)}{((2 + 7) \times (45 + 90))} \\
 &:= \frac{((8 + 1) \times 36)}{(27 \times (45 \times (9 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(8 - (1 - (3 + 6)))}{((2 \times (7 \times 45)) - 90)} &:= \frac{(8 - (1 - (3 - 6)))}{((2 \times (7 \times (4 + 5))) + (9 - 0))} &:= \frac{(8 \times ((1^3) \times 6))}{((2 + (7 + (4 + 5))) \times 90)} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 \times ((1 + 3) \times 6))}{((27 + 45) \times 90)} &:= \frac{(8 \times (1 - (3 - 6)))}{(2 \times ((7 + (4 - 5)) \times 90))} &:= \frac{(8 \times (1 \times (3 \times 6)))}{((2 + (7 + 45)) \times 90)} &:= \frac{(8 \times (1 \times (3 + 6)))}{(((2 \times (7 + 4)) + 5) \times 90)} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 \times (1 \times 36))}{(((2^7) - (4 \times 5)) \times 90)} &:= \frac{(8 \times (1 + (3 \times 6)))}{((2 + ((7 + 4) \times 5)) \times 90)} &:= \frac{(8 \times (1 + (3 + 6)))}{(2 \times ((7 - 4) \times (5 \times 90)))} &:= \frac{(8 \times (13 - 6))}{(2 \times (7 \times (45 + 90)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 \times (1^{36}))}{(2 \times ((7 - 4) \times (5 \times (9 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(8 + (1 - (3 - 6)))}{((2 - 7) \times (4 + (5 - 90)))} &:= \frac{(81 - (3 - 6))}{(2745 + 90)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9028}{153476} &:= \frac{((9 \times (0 \times 2)) + 8)}{(1 + (5 \times (3^4 - 7 + 6)))} &:= \frac{((9 \times (0 + 2)) + 8)}{(((1 + (5 \times 3)) \times (4 \times 7)) - 6)} &:= \frac{((9 \times (0 + 2)) - 8)}{(1 \times (5 - (3 - (4 \times (7 \times 6))))))} &:= \frac{((9 + (0 - 2)) \times 8)}{(1 \times ((5 - 3) \times 476))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 - ((0 \times 2) - 8))}{(1 + ((53 \times 4) + 76))} &:= \frac{(9 - (0 - (2 \times 8)))}{(1 + (((5^3) \times 4) - 76))} &:= \frac{(9 - (0 - (2 - 8)))}{(1 - (5 - (3 + (4 \times (7 + 6))))))} &:= \frac{(9 - (0 \times 28))}{(1 + (5 + ((3 \times 47) + 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 - (0 - 28))}{(153 + 476)} &:= \frac{(9 \times ((0 \times 2) + 8))}{((1 - ((5 - 34) \times 7)) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(9 \times (0 - (2 - 8)))}{(1 + (5 + (3 \times (4 \times 7))))} &:= \frac{(9 \times (0 + (2 + 8)))}{(15 \times (3 \times ((4 \times 7) + 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 \times (0 + 28))}{((1 + (5^3)) \times ((4 \times 7) + 6))} &:= \frac{(9 + ((0 \times 2) - 8))}{(1 \times (5 + (3 \times (4 \times (7 - 6))))))} &:= \frac{(9 + (0 - (2 - 8)))}{(1 \times (5 \times (3 \times (4 + (7 + 6))))))} &:= \frac{(90 + (2 \times 8))}{(1 \times (53 \times ((4 \times 7) + 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(90 + (2^8))}{(1 + (((5^3) \times 47) + 6))} &:= \frac{(90 + (2 - 8))}{((1 + (5 - 3)) \times 476)} &:= \frac{(90 - 28)}{((1^5) + ((3^4) \times (7 + 6)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9603}{182457} &:= \frac{((9 \times (6 - 0)) - 3)}{((1 - (8 - 24)) \times 57)} &:= \frac{((9^6 + 0) \times 3)}{(((1 + 8)^{2+4}) \times 57)} &:= \frac{((9 + (6 - 0)) \times 3)}{((1 + (8 + (2 + 4))) \times 57)} &:= \frac{((9 + 60) \times 3)}{((1 + ((8^2) + 4)) \times 57)} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 - (6 - (0 \times 3)))}{(1 - (8 - (2^4 - 5 + 7)))} &:= \frac{(9 - (6 \times (0 \times 3)))}{((1 + (8 - (2 + 4))) \times 57)} &:= \frac{(9 - (6 + (0 - 3)))}{(1 \times (8 - (2 \times (4 - 57))))} &:= \frac{(9 \times (6 - (0 \times 3)))}{(1 - (8 - (2 + ((4^5) + 7))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 \times (6 \times (0 + 3)))}{((1 + 8) \times ((2 + 4) \times 57))} &:= \frac{(9 \times (6 + (0 - 3)))}{(1 + (8 \times (2^4 - 5 + 7)))} &:= \frac{(9 + (6 - (0 \times 3)))}{(((1^8)^2 + 4) \times 57)} &:= \frac{(9 + (6 - (0 - 3)))}{(1 \times ((8 + (2 - 4)) \times 57))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 + (6 + (0 - 3)))}{(1 + ((8 \times 24) + (5 \times 7)))} &:= \frac{(9 + (60 \times 3))}{((1 + (8^2 - 4 + 5)) \times 7)} &:= \frac{(9 + (60 + 3))}{(1 \times ((8 + (2^4)) \times 57))} &:= \frac{(9 + (60 - 3))}{(((1 + 8) \times 2) + 4) \times 57)} \\
 &:= \frac{(96 - (0 \times 3))}{(1 \times ((8 + 24) \times 57))} &:= \frac{(96 - (0 - 3))}{((1 + (8 + 24)) \times 57)} &:= \frac{(96 + (0 - 3))}{(1824 - 57)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9876}{123450} &:= \frac{(((9 - 8)^7) \times 6)}{(1 - (2 - ((3^4) - (5 - 0))))} &:= \frac{((9 - (8 - 7)) \times 6)}{(1 \times (((2^3) + 4) \times 50))} &:= \frac{((9 \times 8) + 76)}{((1 + (2 + 34)) \times 50)} &:= \frac{((9 + (8 + 7)) \times 6)}{(1 \times ((2 + 34) \times 50))} \\
 &:= \frac{((9 + (8 - 7)) \times 6)}{((1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times 50)} &:= \frac{((9 + 87) \times 6)}{(12 \times (3 \times (4 \times 50)))} &:= \frac{(9 - 8) \times 76}{(1 \times ((23 - 4) \times 50))} &:= \frac{(9 - ((8 - 7)^6))}{((1 + (2 + (3 - 4))) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 - (8 - (7 + 6)))}{(((1^2) + 34) \times (5 - 0))} &:= \frac{(9 - (8 - (7 - 6)))}{(1 + (2 \times (3 + (4 + (5 - 0))))))} &:= \frac{(9 \times ((8 - 7) \times 6))}{(1 \times (((2 + 3)^4) + 50))} &:= \frac{(9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6)))}{(1 \times (234 \times 50))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 \times (8 \times (7 - 6)))}{((1 - (2 - 3)) \times 450)} &:= \frac{(9 + ((8 - 7)^6))}{(1 + (2 \times ((3 \times 4) + 50)))} &:= \frac{(9 + (8 - (7 + 6)))}{(1 - (2 + (3 - (4 + 50))))} &:= \frac{(9 + (8 - (7 - 6)))}{(1 + (2 - (3 - (4 \times 50))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 + (8 + (7 - 6)))}{(1 \times ((2 + 3) \times (45 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(98 - (7 \times 6))}{(1 \times (2 \times ((3 + 4) \times 50)))} &:= \frac{(98 + (7 \times 6))}{(((1^2) + 34) \times 50)}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.19 20 Equivalent Blocks

• Five Digit's Numerator

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{13790}{48265} := \frac{(((1^3)^7) + (9 - 0))}{(4 + (((8 - 2) \times 6) - 5))} := \frac{(((1^3) + 7) \times (9 - 0))}{(4 + (8 \times (26 + 5)))} := \frac{(((1 + 3) \times 7) + 90)}{(((4 + (8^2)) \times 6) + 5)} := \frac{((1^3) - (7 - 90))}{(4 + (((8^2) - 6) \times 5))}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{((1^3) \times (7 + (9 - 0)))}{(4 - (8 - (2 \times (6 \times 5))))} := \frac{((1^3) + (7 \times (9 - 0)))}{(4 \times (8 \times ((2 \times 6) - 5)))} := \frac{((1^3) + (79 - 0))}{((48 + (2 + 6)) \times 5)} := \frac{((1 - 3) \times (7 - (9 - 0)))}{(4 + (8 + (2 \times (6 - 5))))} \\ &:= \frac{((1 - 3) \times (7 - 90))}{((48 \times (2 \times 6)) + 5)} := \frac{(1 - ((3 \times 7) - 90))}{((4 \times (8^2)) - (6 + 5))} := \frac{(1 - (3 - (7 + (9 - 0))))}{(48 + (2 - (6 - 5)))} := \frac{(1 \times ((3 \times 7) + (9 - 0)))}{(4 + ((8 \times (2 \times 6)) + 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (3 + (7 + 90)))}{(((4 \times (8 \times 2)) + 6) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 \times (37 - (9 - 0)))}{(4 + ((8^2) + (6 \times 5)))} := \frac{(1 \times (37 + (9 - 0)))}{((48 \times 2) + 65)} := \frac{(1 + (3 - (7 - (9 - 0))))}{(1 + (3 - (7 - (9 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (3 + (7 + (9 - 0))))}{(4 + ((8 - 2) \times (6 + 5)))} := \frac{(1 + (37 + 90))}{(4 \times (82 + (6 \times 5)))} := \frac{(13 - (7 - 90))}{(48 \times ((2 \times 6) - 5))} := \frac{(137 + (9 - 0))}{(4 + ((8 \times (2^6)) - 5))} \end{aligned}$$

▶ $\frac{18270}{63945}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{((1^{82}) \times 70)}{((6 + (39 + 4)) \times 5)} := \frac{((1^{82}) + (7 - 0))}{(6 - (3 - ((9 - 4) \times 5)))} := \frac{((1^8) - (2 - (7 - 0)))}{(6 - (3 - (9 + (4 + 5))))} := \frac{((1^8) + (27 - 0))}{(6 + (3 + (94 - 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + 8) \times 270)}{((6 + 3) \times 945)} := \frac{(1 - (8 - (2 + (7 - 0))))}{(((6 - 3) \times 9) - (4 \times 5))} := \frac{(1 - (8 - (27 - 0)))}{((6 + (3 + (9 - 4))) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (2 + (7 - 0))))}{((6^3) - (9 - 45))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 + (2 \times (7 - 0))))}{(1 \times (8 + (2 \times (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 \times (82 - 70))}{(1 \times ((8 \times 2) - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + ((8 \times 2) - (7 - 0)))}{(1 + ((8 \times 2) + (7 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(((6 + (3 + 9)) \times 4) + 5)}{(1 + (8 - (2 - (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(6 + ((3 \times 9) + (4 + 5)))}{(1 + (8 + (2 - (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(6 - (((3 - 9) \times 4) - 5))}{(1 + (8 + (2 + (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(6 - (3 - (9 \times (4 + 5))))}{(1 + (8 + (27 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + (((3 + 9) \times 4) - 5))}{(1 + (82 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(6 - (3 + (9 - (4 \times 5))))}{(18 \times 270)} := \frac{(6 + (3 + (9 + 45)))}{(18 + (2 \times (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(6 \times (3 + (9 + (4 + 5))))}{(18 + 270)} \\ &:= \frac{((6^3) + (94 + 5))}{((6^3) + (94 + 5))} := \frac{(6 \times (3 \times 945))}{((6 + 3) \times (9 + 4)) - 5} := \frac{(63 + 945)}{(63 + 945)} \end{aligned}$$

▶ $\frac{19258}{67403}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(1 - ((9 - 2) \times (5 - 8)))}{(6 + (7 + (4^{03})))} := \frac{(1 - (9 - (2 \times (5 + 8))))}{(6 - (7 - (4^{03})))} := \frac{(1 - (9 - (2 + (5 \times 8))))}{(6 - (7 - (40 \times 3)))} := \frac{(1 - (9 + (2 - (5 \times 8))))}{(6 - ((7 - 40) \times 3))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (9 + (2 - 58)))}{(6 \times (7 \times (4 - (0 \times 3))))} := \frac{(1 \times ((9^2) - (5 - 8)))}{(6 \times (7 \times (4 - (0 - 3))))} := \frac{(1 \times (9 - (2 - (5 - 8))))}{(6 + (7 + (4 + (0 - 3))))} := \frac{(1 \times (9 - (2 + (5 - 8))))}{((6 \times 7) - (4 - (0 - 3)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (9 + (2 - (5 - 8))))}{(((6 + 7) \times (4 - 0)) - 3)} := \frac{(1 \times (9 + (2 + (5 + 8))))}{(6 \times (7 + (4 - (0 - 3))))} := \frac{(1 \times (9 + (25 + 8)))}{(6 + ((7 + 40) \times 3))} := \frac{(1 \times (9 + (25 - 8)))}{((6 + 7) \times (4 - (0 - 3)))} \\ &:= \frac{((6 \times (74 - (0 - 3))))}{(1 \times (92 + (5 \times 8)))} := \frac{(1 + ((9 \times 2) - (5 + 8)))}{(1 + ((9 \times 2) \times (5 + 8)))} := \frac{(6 \times (7 \times (4 \times (0 + 3))))}{((6 \times (7 - (4 - 0))) + 3)} := \frac{(6 + (7 + (40 + 3)))}{(1 + (9 - (2 \times (5 - 8))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (9 + ((2 \times 5) - 8)))}{(6 \times (7^{4-03}))} := \frac{(1 + (9 + (2 \times 58)))}{((6 \times (74 - 0)) - 3)} := \frac{(19 \times ((2 \times 5) - 8))}{(6 + (7 + (40 \times 3)))} := \frac{(192 - 58)}{(67 \times (4 - (0 - 3)))} \end{aligned}$$

▶ $\frac{19560}{27384}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(((1^9) + 5) \times 60)}{(2 \times (7 \times (3 \times (8 + 4))))} := \frac{(((1^{95}) \times 60)}{(2 \times (7 + (3 + (8 \times 4))))} := \frac{((1 + (9 - 5)) \times (6 - 0))}{(2 + ((7 + 3) \times (8 - 4)))} := \frac{((1 + 9) \times (5 + (6 - 0)))}{(2 \times (73 + (8 - 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{((1 - 9) \times (5 - 60))}{(2 \times (7 \times ((3 + 8) \times 4)))} := \frac{((19 + 5) \times 60)}{((27 - 3) \times 84)} := \frac{(1 \times ((9 \times 5) + 60))}{(2 - (7 - (38 \times 4)))} := \frac{(1 \times ((9 + 5) \times 60))}{(1 \times ((9 + 5) \times 60))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (9 \times (5 \times (6 - 0))))}{((2 + 7) \times (38 + 4))} := \frac{(1 \times (9 + (5 + (6 - 0))))}{(2 \times (7 + (3 + (8 - 4))))} := \frac{(1 \times (95 - 60))}{((27 \times 3) - (8 \times 4))} := \frac{(1 + ((9 + 5) \times (6 - 0)))}{((2^7) + (3 - (8 + 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + ((9 - 5) \times (6 - 0)))}{(2 + ((7 \times 3) + (8 + 4)))} := \frac{(1 + (9 - (5 - 60)))}{(2 - (7 - (3 \times (8 \times 4))))} := \frac{(1 + (9 \times (5 + (6 - 0))))}{((2^7) + (3 \times (8 - 4)))} := \frac{(1 + (9 + (5 \times (6 - 0))))}{((2 + (7 - (3 - 8))) \times 4)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (9 + (5 + 60)))}{(2 + (7 + (3 \times (8 \times 4))))} := \frac{(1 + (95 - (6 - 0)))}{(2 - ((7 - 38) \times 4))} := \frac{(195 + 60)}{(2 + ((7^3) + (8 + 4)))} := \frac{(195 - 60)}{(27 \times (3 + (8 - 4)))} \end{aligned}$$

▶ $\frac{20835}{91674}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{((2 - (0 - (8 - 3))) \times 5)}{((9 - (1 - 6)) \times (7 + 4))} := \frac{((2 - (0 - 8)) \times (3 \times 5))}{((9 + 1) \times (6 \times (7 + 4)))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 \times 83)) + 5)}{((9 \times (1 - (6 - 7))) + 4)} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + (8 - 3))) + 5)}{(((9 + (1^6)) \times 7) - 4)} \\ &:= \frac{((2^{0 \times 8 + 3}) \times 5)}{(9 - (1 - (6 \times (7 \times 4))))} := \frac{((2^{08-3}) \times 5)}{((9 + 167) \times 4)} := \frac{((20 \times (8 + 3)) + 5)}{(916 + 74)} := \frac{((20 + (8 + 3)) \times 5)}{(9 - (1 - 674))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (8 + (3 \times 5))))}{((9 + (1^6)) \times (7 + 4))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (83 + 5)))}{(9 \times (16 + (7 \times 4)))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (83 - 5)))}{(9 + ((1 + 6)^{7-4}))} := \frac{(2 \times ((0 \times 8) + (3 \times 5)))}{(((9 - (1 + 6))^7) + 4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(2 \times ((0 \times 8) + 35))}{((9 + (1 + 67)) \times 4)} := \frac{(2 \times ((0 \times 83) + 5))}{(9 + (1 + (6 + (7 \times 4))))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + ((8 + 3) \times 5)))}{((9 + (16 \times 7)) \times 4)} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + ((8 - 3) \times 5)))}{(((9 - 1) \times 6) + 7) \times 4)} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (8 - (3 - 5))))}{(9 - (1 - (6 + 74)))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (8 \times 35)))}{((9 \times (1 + 6)) + (7^4))} := \frac{(20 \times (8 + (3 - 5)))}{((9 - 1) \times (6 \times (7 + 4)))} := \frac{(20 + (8 \times (3 \times 5)))}{((9 \times (1 + 67)) + 4)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{21036}{57849} & := \frac{((2 - (1 + (0 - 3))) \times 6)}{(5 + ((7 \times 8) - (4 - 9)))} := \frac{((2 \times 103) + 6)}{(578 - (4 - 9))} := \frac{((2 + (10 \times 3)) \times 6)}{((5 + 7) \times (8 + (4 \times 9)))} := \frac{((2 + 10) \times (3 + 6))}{((5 + (7 \times (8 - 4))) \times 9)} \\
 & := \frac{((21 - (0 - 3)) \times 6)}{((5 + (7 + (8 \times 4))) \times 9)} := \frac{(2 - (1 - (0 - (3 - 6))))}{(5 - (7 - (8 - (4 - 9))))} := \frac{(2 - (10 \times (3 - 6)))}{(5 + (78 - (4 - 9)))} := \frac{(2 \times ((1 - (0 - 3)) \times 6))}{(5 + (78 + 49))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times ((10 + 3) \times 6))}{((5 \times (7 \times (8 + 4))) + 9)} := \frac{(2 \times ((10 - 3) \times 6))}{((5 \times (7 \times 8)) - 49)} := \frac{(2 \times (1 - (0 - (3 + 6))))}{(5 - (7 - (8 + 49)))} := \frac{(2 \times (1 \times (0 + (3 \times 6))))}{(((5 \times 7) - 8) \times 4) - 9)} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times (1 + (0 - (3 - 6))))}{(((5 \times 7) - (8 - (4 - 9))))} := \frac{(2 \times (10 \times (3 + 6)))}{(5 \times ((7 + (8 - 4)) \times 9))} := \frac{(2 \times (10 + 36))}{(((5 + (7 \times 8)) \times 4) + 9)} := \frac{(2^{1^{03 \times 6}})}{(5 + ((7 + (8 + 4)) \times 9))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times (1 + (0 - (3 - 6))))}{((5 \times (7 - 8)) + 49)} := \frac{(2 + ((10 + 3) \times 6))}{(5 + ((7 \times (8 \times 4)) - 9))} := \frac{(2 + (1 - (0 - (3 + 6))))}{(5 + (7 + (8 + (4 + 9))))} := \frac{210 + 3 \times 6}{578 + 49} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{28539}{76104} & := \frac{(((2^8 - 5) \times 3) - 9)}{((7 - 6) \times (10 \times 4))} := \frac{(((2 + 8) \times (5 \times 3)) + 9)}{((7 \times (6 \times 10)) + 4)} := \frac{(((28 - 5) \times 3) + 9)}{(((7 \times 6) + 10) \times 4)} := \frac{((2 - (8 - (5 \times 3))) \times 9)}{((7 - 61) \times (0 - 4))} \\
 & := \frac{((2 - (8 - 5)) \times (3 - 9))}{(7 + (6 - (1 + (0 - 4))))} := \frac{((2 \times ((8 - 5)^3)) + 9)}{(7 \times (6 \times (1 \times (0 + 4))))} := \frac{((2 + (8 \times 5)) \times 39)}{(7 \times (6 \times 104))} := \frac{((2 + (8 - 5)) \times 39)}{((7 + 6) \times (10 \times 4))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 - (8 - (5 \times (3 \times 9))))}{((76 + 10) \times 4)} := \frac{(2 - (8 + (5 \times (3 - 9))))}{(7 + (61 + (0 - 4)))} := \frac{(2 \times (8 - (5 - (3 + 9))))}{(2 \times (8 - (5 - (3 + 9))))} := \frac{((7 + (6 - (1 - 0))) \times 4)}{(2 + (85 + (3 \times 9)))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 + (8 + (5 - (3 + 9))))}{(7 + (6 - (1 - (0 - 4))))} := \frac{(2 + (8 + (5 - (3 - 9))))}{((7 + (6 + (1 - 0))) \times 4)} := \frac{(2 + (8 + (5 + (3 + 9))))}{(7 + (61 - (0 - 4)))} := \frac{(2 + (85 + (3 \times 9)))}{(76 \times (1 \times (0 + 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 + (85 + (3 + 9)))}{((76 - 10) \times 4)} := \frac{(2 + (85 - 39))}{(((7 \times 6) - 10) \times 4)} := \frac{(28 \times ((5 \times 3) - 9))}{(7 \times ((6 + 10) \times 4))} := \frac{(28 + (5 - (3 - 9)))}{((7 - 6) \times 104)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30165}{78429} & := \frac{((3 - (0 - (1 \times 6))) \times 5)}{((7 + (8 - (4 - 2))) \times 9)} := \frac{((3 - (0 - (1 + 6))) \times 5)}{(((7 + (8 - 4))^2) + 9)} := \frac{((3 - (0 - 16)) \times 5)}{((7 \times ((8 \times 4) + 2)) + 9)} := \frac{((3 + (0 - (1^6))) \times 5)}{(7 + (8 + (4 - (2 - 9))))} \\
 & := \frac{((30 - (1^6)) \times 5)}{(7 - (8 - (42 \times 9)))} := \frac{((30 \times (1 + 6)) + 5)}{((7 \times 84) - 29)} := \frac{((30 - 16) \times 5)}{(7 \times (8 + ((4 - 2) \times 9)))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (1 + (6 + 5))))}{((7 \times (8 - 4)) + (2 + 9))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 - (0 - (1 + (6 - 5))))}{(7 - (8 + (4 - (2 \times 9))))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 - ((1 - 6) \times 5)))}{((7 \times (8 \times 4)) - 29)} := \frac{(3 \times (0 - (1 - (6 + 5))))}{(((7 + 8) \times 4) + (2 \times 9))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + ((1 + 6) \times 5)))}{(7 \times ((8 \times (4 + 2)) - 9))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (1 \times (6 \times 5))))}{(((7 \times (8 - 4)) - 2) \times 9)} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (1 \times 65)))}{(7 - (8 + (4 - (2^9))))} := \frac{(30 - ((1^6) \times 5))}{((7 \times ((8 - 4) \times 2)) + 9)} := \frac{(30 - ((1 - 6) \times 5))}{(7 - (8 - ((4^2) \times 9)))} \\
 & := \frac{(30 \times (1 \times (6 + 5)))}{(7 + (842 + 9))} := \frac{(30 \times (1 + (6 + 5)))}{(((7 \times 8) - 4) \times (2 \times 9))} := \frac{(30 \times (16 + 5))}{((7 + 84) \times (2 \times 9))} := \frac{(30 + ((1^6) \times 5))}{(7 - ((8 + 4) \times (2 - 9)))} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30168}{52794} & := \frac{((3 - (0 - (1 + 6))) \times 8)}{(5 \times ((2 \times (7 + 9)) - 4))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 \times 1)) + (6 \times 8))}{((5^2) + ((7 \times 9) - 4))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 \times 1)) + 68)}{(5 \times ((2 \times 7) + 9)) + 4)} := \frac{((3 \times (0 \times 16)) + 8)}{(5 - (27 - (9 \times 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{((3 \times (0 + 16)) + 8)}{(5 + (2 + (7 \times (9 + 4))))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 + 16)) - 8)}{(5 \times (2 + (7 + (9 - 4))))} := \frac{((3 + (0 - (1^6))))^8}{((5 + 2) \times ((7 + 9) \times 4))} := \frac{((3 + (0 - (1 - 6))) \times 8)}{((5 + ((2 \times 7) + 9)) \times 4)} \\
 & := \frac{((3 + (0 - 1)) \times (6 + 8))}{((5 + 2)^{7-9+4})} := \frac{((30 \times (1 \times 6)) + 8)}{(5 + ((2 + 79) \times 4))} := \frac{((30 \times (1 \times 6)) - 8)}{(5 + 2) \times (7 + (9 \times 4))} := \frac{((30 + (1 \times 6)) \times 8)}{((5 \times 27) - 9) \times 4)} \\
 & := \frac{((30 + (1 - 6)) \times 8)}{(5 \times (2 \times (7 \times (9 - 4))))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - ((1^6) + 8)))}{(5 - (2 \times ((7 - 9) \times 4))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (1 + (6 \times 8))))}{(5 + (2 \times (7 + (9 \times 4))))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (1 + 68)))}{(5 + (27 + 94))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (1 \times (6 \times 8))))}{(5 + ((27 \times 9) + 4))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (16 - 8)))}{(5 + (2 + (7 \times (9 - 4))))} := \frac{(30 \times (1 \times (6 \times 8)))}{(5 \times (2 \times (7 \times (9 \times 4))))} := \frac{(30 + (1 \times (6 + 8)))}{(5 + ((2 + (7 + 9)) \times 4))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{31095}{74628} &:= \frac{(((3 \times 10) - 9) \times 5)}{(7 \times (4 + ((6 - 2) \times 8)))} := \frac{((3 - (1 \times (0 - 9))) \times 5)}{((7 - (4 - 6)) \times (2 \times 8))} := \frac{((3 - (1^{09})) \times 5)}{((7 + (4 - (6 + 2))) \times 8)} := \frac{((3 - (1 + (0 - 9))) \times 5)}{((7 \times ((4 + 6) \times 2)) - 8)} \\ &:= \frac{((3 - (1 - 0)) \times (9 \times 5))}{((7 \times (4 \times (6 + 2))) - 8)} := \frac{((3 \times (1 + 09)) + 5)}{(7 \times ((4 - 6) \times (2 - 8)))} := \frac{((3 \times (1 + 09)) - 5)}{((7 \times (4 + 6)) - (2 + 8))} := \frac{((3 \times (1 \times (0 \times 9))) + 5)}{((7 - 4) \times ((6 \times 2) - 8))} \\ &:= \frac{((3 + (1^{09})) \times 5)}{((7 + 4) \times (6 \times (2 + 8)))} := \frac{((3 + (10 + 9)) \times 5)}{((7 \times (46 \times 2)) - 8)} := \frac{(3 \times (1 - (0 - (9 + 5))))}{((7 - 4) \times (6 \times (2 + 8)))} := \frac{(3 \times (1 - (0 - (9 - 5))))}{((7 \times (46 - 2)) - 8)} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (1 \times (0 + (9 \times 5))))}{(74 - (6 - (2^8)))} := \frac{(3 \times (10 \times (9^5)))}{(((7 - 4)^6)^2 \times 8)} := \frac{(3 \times (10 \times (9 - 5)))}{((7 \times (4 + (6^2))) + 8)} := \frac{(3 \times (10 + 95))}{(7 \times (((4 + 6)^2) + 8))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{31824}{79560} &:= \frac{((3 - (1 - (8^2))) \times 4)}{((7 + (9 - 5)) \times 60)} := \frac{((3 - (1 - (8 - 2))) \times 4)}{(79 - (5 - (6 - 0)))} := \frac{((3 \times (1 \times 82)) - 4)}{((7 \times 95) - 60)} := \frac{((3 + (1 + (8 + 2))) \times 4)}{(7 \times (9 + (5 + (6 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{((3 + 18) \times 24)}{((7 + (9 + 5)) \times 60)} := \frac{((31 \times (8 - 2)) - 4)}{(7 \times (9 + (56 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 - (1 - (8 + (2 - 4))))}{(((7 + 9) \times 5) - 60)} := \frac{(3 - (1^{824}))}{(7 + (9 - (5 + (6 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (1 \times (8 \times (2 \times 4))))}{((7 + 9) \times (5 \times (6 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 \times (1 \times (8 + (2^4))))}{((7 - (9 - 5)) \times 60)} := \frac{(3 \times (18 + (2^4)))}{((7 \times (9 \times 5)) - 60)} := \frac{(3 + (1 - (8 - 24)))}{(((7 - 9) \times 5) + 60)} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (1 + ((8 + 2) \times 4)))}{((7 - 9) \times (5 - 60))} := \frac{(3 + (1 + (8 - (2 + 4))))}{(7 + (9 + (5 - (6 - 0))))} := \frac{(3 + (1 + (8 + (2^4))))}{(7 \times (9 - (5 - (6 - 0))))} := \frac{(3 + (1 + (8 + 24)))}{(79 + (5 + (6 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(31 \times (8 + (2 + 4)))}{(7 \times (95 + 60))} := \frac{(318 \times (2 + 4))}{(795 \times (6 - 0))} := \frac{(318 + 24)}{(795 + 60)} := \frac{(318 - 24)}{(7 \times ((9 \times 5) + 60))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{38092}{47615} &:= \frac{((3 - (8 + (0 - 9))) \times 2)}{(4 + (7 - (6 - (1 \times 5))))} := \frac{((3 - (8 + (0 - 9)))^2)}{(4 + (7 - (6 - 15)))} := \frac{((3 \times (8 - 0)) + 92)}{((4 \times (7 \times (6 - 1))) + 5)} := \frac{((3 + (8 - (0 - 9))) \times 2)}{(4 + ((7 \times 6) - (1 - 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{((3 + (80 + 9)) \times 2)}{((4 + (7 \times (6 \times 1))) \times 5)} := \frac{(3 - (8 + (0 - (9^2))))}{(4 + (76 + 15))} := \frac{(3 \times (8 - (0 \times 92)))}{((4 + (7 - (6 - 1))) \times 5)} := \frac{(3 \times (8 \times ((0 \times 9) + 2)))}{(4 \times ((7 - 6) \times 15))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (8 \times (0 + (9 \times 2))))}{((47 + 61) \times 5)} := \frac{(3 \times (8 \times (0 + (9 + 2))))}{((4 + 7) \times (6 \times (1 \times 5)))} := \frac{(3 \times (8 \times (0 + (9 - 2))))}{((47 - (6 - 1)) \times 5)} := \frac{(3 \times (8^{0 \times 9 + 2}))}{(4 \times ((7 + (6 - 1)) \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (8 - (0 - (9^2))))}{(((4 \times 7) - (6 - 1)) \times 5)} := \frac{(3 + (8 + (0 - (9 - 2))))}{(4 + (7 - (6 \times (1^5))))} := \frac{(3 + (80 - (9 + 2)))}{((4 + (7 + (6 + 1))) \times 5)} := \frac{(3 + (80 + (9^2)))}{((47 - (6 \times 1)) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(38 - (0 - (9 \times 2)))}{(((4 + 7) \times 6) - (1 - 5))} := \frac{(38 + ((0 \times 9) - 2))}{((4 - (7 - 6)) \times 15)} := \frac{(38 + (0 - (9 \times 2)))}{((4 + (7 - (6 \times 1))) \times 5)} := \frac{(380 - 92)}{((4 + (7 + 61)) \times 5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{54328}{67910} &:= \frac{(((5 \times (4 \times 3)) - 2) \times 8)}{((67 - 9) \times 10)} := \frac{(((5 + 43) \times 2) + 8)}{((6 + 7) \times (9 + (1 - 0)))} := \frac{((5 - (4 - (3 \times 2))) \times 8)}{(6 + ((7 \times 9) + (1 - 0)))} := \frac{((5 - (4 - 32)) \times 8)}{(((6 \times 7) - 9) \times 10)} \\ &:= \frac{((5 \times (4^3)) + (2 \times 8))}{(6 \times (7 \times (9 + (1 - 0))))} := \frac{((5^4) - ((3^2) + 8))}{((67 + 9) \times 10)} := \frac{((5 + ((4^3) - 2)) \times 8)}{(67 \times (9 + (1 - 0)))} := \frac{((5 + (4 - (3 - 2))) \times 8)}{((6 - (7 - 9)) \times 10)} \\ &:= \frac{((5 + (4 \times (3 - 2))) \times 8)}{((6 \times (7 + (9 - (1 - 0))))} := \frac{((5 + 43) \times (2 \times 8))}{(6 \times ((7 + 9) \times 10))} := \frac{((54 - (3 \times 2)) \times 8)}{(6 \times (79 + (1 - 0)))} := \frac{((54 - 32) \times 8)}{((6 + (7 + 9)) \times 10)} \\ &:= \frac{(5 - (4 - (3 + 28)))}{((6 + (7 - 9)) \times 10)} := \frac{(5 - (4 + (3 + (2 - 8))))}{(6 + (7 - (9 - (1 - 0))))} := \frac{(5 \times ((4 \times 32) + 8))}{((6 + 79) \times 10)} := \frac{(5 \times (4 \times (3 + (2 \times 8))))}{((6 \times 79) + (1 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 \times (4 + ((3 - 2) \times 8)))}{(6 + (79 - 10))} := \frac{(5 + (4 + (3 + 28)))}{((6 \times 7) + (9 - (1 - 0)))} := \frac{(5 + (43 + 28))}{(6 + (79 + 10))} := \frac{(54 + ((3 \times 2) + 8))}{(6 + (79 \times (1 - 0)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{57429}{63810} := \frac{(((5 \times (7 - 4))^2) + 9)}{(((6 \times 3) + 8) \times 10)} := \frac{(((5 \times (7 - 4))^2) - 9)}{((6 - 3) \times (8 \times 10))} := \frac{(((5 \times (7 - 4)) + 2) \times 9)}{((6 + (3 + 8)) \times 10)} := \frac{(((5 + 7) \times (4 + 2)) + 9)}{(6 + (3 + (81 - 0)))}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((5+7)^{4-2}) \times 9)}{(6 \times (3 \times (8 \times 10)))} &:= \frac{((5 \times (7 + (4 - 2))) - 9)}{(6 + ((3 \times 8) + 10))} &:= \frac{((5 + ((7 - 4) \times 2)) \times 9)}{((6 - (3 - 8)) \times 10)} &:= \frac{((5 + (7 \times 4)) \times (2 \times 9))}{(6 \times ((3 + 8) \times 10))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 + 7) \times ((4 + 2) \times 9))}{((6 + 3) \times (8 \times 10))} &:= \frac{((5 + 7) \times (4 + 29))}{((6 + 38) \times 10)} &:= \frac{((5 + 7) \times (42 \times 9))}{(63 \times (8 \times 10))} &:= \frac{((57 - (4 - 2)) \times 9)}{((63 - 8) \times 10)} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 - (7 - (4 - (2 - 9))))}{(6 - (3 - (8 - (1 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(5 - (7 \times (4 - (2 + 9))))}{(6 + (3 \times (8 + 10)))} &:= \frac{(5 \times ((7 - 4) \times (2 \times 9)))}{((6 + (3 \times 8)) \times 10)} &:= \frac{(5 \times (7 + (4 - (2 - 9))))}{(((6 \times 3) - 8) \times 10)} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (((7 + 4) \times 2) - 9))}{(6 + ((3 \times 8) - 10))} &:= \frac{(5 + (((7 + 4)^2) + 9))}{(6 \times ((3 \times 8) + (1 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(5 + (7 + (4 + (2 + 9))))}{(6 \times (3 - (8 - 10)))} &:= \frac{(5 + (7 + (42 + 9)))}{(63 + (8 - (1 - 0)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{58496}{73120}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((5 - 8) \times 4) + 96)}{(7 \times (3 + (12 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(((5 - (8 - (4 + 9))) \times 6)}{(73 + (1 \times (2 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(((5 - (8 + (4 - 9)))^6)}{((7 - (3 \times 1)) \times 20)} &:= \frac{((5 - (8 - 4)) \times 96)}{((7 + 3) \times (12 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 - (8 - 49)) \times 6)}{((7^3 \times 1) + (2 - 0))} &:= \frac{((5 + ((8 \times 4) - 9)) \times 6)}{((7 + 3) \times (1 + 20))} &:= \frac{((5 + (8 + (4 - 9))) \times 6)}{((7 - (3 + 1)) \times 20)} &:= \frac{(5 - (8 - (4 + (9 + 6))))}{((7 + (3 \times 1)) \times (2 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 - (8 - (4 + (9 - 6))))}{(7 - (3 - (1^2 + 0)))} &:= \frac{(5 - (8 + (4 - (9 + 6))))}{(7 + (3 \times (1^2 + 0)))} &:= \frac{(5 \times ((8 - 4)^{9-6})}{(((7 \times 3) - 1) \times 20)} &:= \frac{(5 + (8 - (4 - (9 + 6))))}{(7 + (3 + (1 \times 20)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (8 - (4 - (9 - 6))))}{(7 + ((3 + 1) \times (2 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(5 + (8 + (4 + (9 + 6))))}{(7 + (31 + (2 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(5 + (8 + (4 + (9 - 6))))}{(7 - (3 - (1 + 20)))} &:= \frac{(5 + (8 + (49 + 6)))}{(73 + (12 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (8 + (49 - 6)))}{(7 + (3 \times (1 + 20)))} &:= \frac{(5 + (84 + (9 + 6)))}{(7 + (3 + 120))} &:= \frac{(58 + ((4 - 9) \times 6))}{(7 \times (3 + (1 \times (2 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(58 + (49 \times 6))}{(((7 \times 3) + 1) \times 20)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{67512}{84390}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((6 - (7 - 51)) \times 2)}{((8 \times 4) + (3 + 90))} &:= \frac{(((6 \times (7 + (5 \times 1)))^2)}{((8 + (4^3)) \times 90)} &:= \frac{(((6^{7-5}) \times (1 + 2))}{((8 + (4 + 3)) \times (9 - 0))} &:= \frac{(((6 + (7 - (5 \times 1)))^2)}{(8 \times (4 - (3 - (9 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((6 + (7 + 5)) \times (1 + 2))}{((84 - 3) \times 90)} &:= \frac{(6 - (7 - (5 \times (1^2))))}{(8 - ((4 \times 3) - (9 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(6 - (7 - (5 + 12)))}{((8 \times 4) - (3 + (9 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(6 - (7 - (51 + 2)))}{((8 \times (4 + 3)) + (9 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times ((7 + (5 \times 1))^2)}{(8 - 4) \times (3 \times 90))} &:= \frac{(6 \times (7 - (5 - 12)))}{(8 + (4 + (3 + 90)))} &:= \frac{(6 \times (7 \times ((5 + 1) \times 2))}{((8 - (4 - 3)) \times 90)} &:= \frac{(6 \times (7 \times (5 \times 12)))}{(((8 \times 4) + 3) \times 90)} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (7 \times (5 + (1^2))))}{(((8 \times 4) + 3) \times (9 - 0))} &:= \frac{(6 \times (7 + (5 \times (1^2))))}{((8 - (4 + 3)) \times 90)} &:= \frac{(6 \times (7 + (5 + 12)))}{((8 + (4 \times 3)) \times (9 - 0))} &:= \frac{(6^{7-5 \times 1^2})}{(84 - (39 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 + ((7 \times 5) + (1 + 2)))}{(8 - (43 - 90))} &:= \frac{(6 + (7 - (5 \times (1^2))))}{(8 - (4 + (3 - (9 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(6 + (7 \times (5 + (1^2))))}{(8 + (43 + (9 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(67 \times (5 - (1^2)))}{((8 \times 43) - (9 - 0))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{71632}{89540}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((7 - (1^6)) \times 3)^2)}{((89 \times 5) - 40)} &:= \frac{(((7 + (1^6))^3) \times 2)}{(8 \times ((9 - 5) \times 40))} &:= \frac{(((7 - (1 - (6 \times 3)))^2)}{((8 \times 95) - 40)} &:= \frac{(((7 - (1 - 6)) \times 32)}{((8 + (9 - 5)) \times 40)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((7 \times (1 \times (6 \times 3))) + 2)}{((8 - (9 - 5)) \times 40)} &:= \frac{(((7 + (1 \times (6 + 3)))^2)}{((8 \times (9 \times 5)) - 40)} &:= \frac{(((7 + (1 \times (6 - 3)))^2)}{(((8 + 9) \times 5) + 40)} &:= \frac{(((7 + (1^{63}))^2)}{(8 \times (9 + (5 - (4 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((7 - 1) \times ((6^3) \times 2))}{(8 \times (9 \times (5 + 40)))} &:= \frac{(((7 - 1) \times (6 \times 32))}{(8 \times (9 \times (5 \times (4 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(((71 + 6) \times 32)}{(((8 \times 9) + 5) \times 40)} &:= \frac{(7 - (1 - (6 \times (3 + 2))))}{(((8 + 9) \times 5) - 40)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 - (1 + (6 - 32)))}{(8 \times ((9 \times 5) - 40))} &:= \frac{(7 \times (1 - (6 - (3^2))))}{(89 - (54 - 0))} &:= \frac{(7 \times (16 \times 32))}{(8 \times ((9 + 5) \times 40))} &:= \frac{(7 + (((1 + 6)^3) + 2))}{(8 \times (95 - 40))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (1 \times (63 + 2)))}{(89 + (5 - (4 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(7 + (1 + 632))}{((8 \times 95) + 40)} &:= \frac{(716 + 32)}{(895 + 40)} &:= \frac{(716 - 32)}{(895 - 40)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{73456}{91820}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((7 - ((3 - 4) \times 5)) \times 6)}{(9 \times (1 \times (8 + (2 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(((7 - (3 - (4 \times 5))) \times 6)}{(9 \times (18 + (2 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(((7 - (3 \times (4 - 5))) \times 6)}{(91 - (8 \times (2 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(((7 \times (3 + (4 - 5))) + 6)}{(9 + (1 \times (8 \times (2 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((7 + ((3 - 4) \times 5)) \times 6)}{(9 + (1 \times (8 - (2 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(((7 + (3 \times (4 - 5))) \times 6)}{(9 + ((1^8) + 20))} &:= \frac{(((7 - 3)^{4-5+6})}{((9 - 1) \times (8 \times 20))} &:= \frac{(((73 + (4 - 5)) \times 6)}{((9 + 18) \times 20)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{(7 - (3 - (4 \times (5 \times 6))))}{(91 + (8^2 + 0))} := \frac{(7 - (3 - (4 \times (5 + 6))))}{((9 + 1) \times (8 - (2 - 0)))} := \frac{(7 - (3 - (4 + 56)))}{((9 - 1) \times (8 + (2 - 0)))} := \frac{(7 - (3 + (4 \times (5 - 6))))}{(9 + (1^{820}))} \\ & := \frac{(7 - (3 + (4 - 56)))}{((9 \times (1 \times 8)) - (2 - 0))} := \frac{(7 + ((3 \times 45) - 6))}{(9 + (1 + (8 \times 20)))} := \frac{(7 + ((3^4) - 56))}{((9 + (1 - 8)) \times 20)} := \frac{(7 + (3 - (4 - (5 \times 6))))}{(9 + (18 \times (2 - 0)))} \\ & := \frac{(7 + (3 \times (4 + (5 - 6))))}{(9 - (1 + (8 - 20)))} := \frac{(7 + (3 \times (45 + 6)))}{((9 + (1^8)) \times 20)} := \frac{(73 - (4 - (5 + 6)))}{((9 + (1^8))^2 + 0)} := \frac{(73 - (4 - (5 - 6)))}{(91 - (8 - (2 - 0)))} \end{aligned}$$

• **Four Digit's Numerator**

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{3192}{408576} & := \frac{(((3 + 1)^9) \times 2)}{(4 \times ((0 - (8 \times (5 - 7)))^6))} := \frac{(((3 - 1)^9) \times 2)}{(4 \times (0 + (8^{5 \times (7-6)})))} := \frac{(((3 - 1)^9)^2)}{((4 \times (0 + 8))^{5 \times (7-6)})} := \frac{((3 \times (1 \times 9)) - 2)}{(40 \times (8 + ((5 + 7) \times 6)))} \\ & := \frac{((3 \times (1 + 9)) + 2)}{(4^{0 \times 857+6})} := \frac{((3 + (1 \times 9))^2)}{(4 \times (0 + (8 \times 576)))} := \frac{((3 + (1^9)) \times 2)}{(4^{0 \times 8+5 \times (7-6)})} := \frac{((3 - 1) \times (9^2))}{((4 - (0 - 8))^{5-7+6})} \\ & := \frac{((3 - 1)^{9-2})}{(4 \times (0 + (8^{5-7+6})))} := \frac{(3 - ((1^9) \times 2))}{(4 \times (0 + (8 \times (5 - (7 - 6)))))} := \frac{(3 - (1^{92}))}{(4^{08-5+7-6})} := \frac{(3 \times (1 \times (9 \times 2)))}{((4 - (0 - 8)) \times 576)} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times (1 \times (9 - 2)))}{((4^{08-5}) \times (7 \times 6))} := \frac{(3^{1^9+2})}{((40 + 8) \times ((5 + 7) \times 6))} := \frac{(3 \times (1^{92}))}{(4 \times (0 - (8 \times ((5 - 7) \times 6))))} := \frac{(3 + ((1^9) \times 2))}{(40 \times (8 - (5 - (7 + 6))))} \\ & := \frac{(3 + (1 \times (9 - 2)))}{(40 \times (8 \times (5 - (7 - 6))))} := \frac{(3 + (1 \times 92))}{(4 \times (0 + (8 \times (5 \times 76))))} := \frac{(3 + (1 + (9 + 2)))}{(40 \times (8 \times (5 + (7 - 6))))} := \frac{(31 + (9 - 2))}{((4^{08-5}) \times 76)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{3297}{145068} & := \frac{(((3 - 2)^9) + 7)}{(1 \times (4 \times ((5 - (0 - 6)) \times 8)))} := \frac{((3 \times (2 + 9)) + 7)}{((1 + 4) \times ((50 - 6) \times 8))} := \frac{((3 \times 2) + (9 + 7))}{((1 - (4 \times (5 \times (0 - 6)))) \times 8)} := \frac{((3^2) \times (9 - 7))}{((14 \times (50 + 6)) + 8)} \\ & := \frac{((3 + 2) \times (9 - 7))}{((1 + ((4 + (5 - 0)) \times 6)) \times 8)} := \frac{((3 - 2) \times (9 - 7))}{(1 \times (4 \times ((5 \times (0 + 6)) - 8)))} := \frac{((3 - 2)^{9-7})}{(1 \times (4 - (5 \times ((0 \times 6) - 8))))} := \frac{(3 - (2 - (9 + 7)))}{((14 \times 50) + (6 \times 8))} \\ & := \frac{(3 - (2 - (9 - 7)))}{(1 \times ((4 \times 50) - 68))} := \frac{(3 - (2 - 97))}{(14 \times ((50 \times 6) + 8))} := \frac{(3 \times ((2 \times 9) - 7))}{(1450 - (6 - 8))} := \frac{(3 \times (2^9-7))}{(14 + (506 + 8))} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times (2 + (9 + 7)))}{((1 - (4 - (50 \times 6))) \times 8)} := \frac{(3 + ((2 \times 9) + 7))}{(1 \times (4 \times ((50 \times 6) + 8)))} := \frac{(3 + ((2 \times 9) - 7))}{((1 - 45) \times (0 - (6 + 8)))} := \frac{(3 + (2 \times (9 + 7)))}{((1 + 4) \times ((50 \times 6) + 8))} \\ & := \frac{(3 + (2^9-7))}{(14 \times ((5 \times (0 + 6)) - 8))} := \frac{(3 + (2 + (9 \times 7)))}{((1 - 45) \times (0 - 68))} := \frac{(32 - (9 + 7))}{(1 \times (4 + (50 \times (6 + 8))))} := \frac{(32 + (9 + 7))}{((1 - 45) \times (0 - (6 \times 8)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{3816}{457920} & := \frac{((3 \times (8 + 1)) + 6)}{(45 \times (7 + (9^2 + 0)))} := \frac{((3 \times 8) - 16)}{((4 + ((5 \times 7) + 9)) \times 20)} := \frac{(3 - (8 - (1 \times 6)))}{(4 \times (5 + (7 + (9 \times (2 - 0)))))} := \frac{(3 - (8 - (1 + 6)))}{(4 \times ((5 + (7 - 9)) \times 20))} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times (8 - (1^6)))}{(4 \times (5 \times (7 \times (9 \times (2 - 0)))))} := \frac{(3 \times (8 \times (1 + 6)))}{(((4^5) - (7 + 9)) \times 20)} := \frac{(3 \times (8 \times (1^6)))}{((4 + (5 + 7)) \times (9 \times 20))} := \frac{(3 \times (8 + (1 - 6)))}{((4 - (5 - 7)) \times (9 \times 20))} \\ & := \frac{(3 \times (8 + 16))}{(4 \times ((5 + 7) \times (9 \times 20)))} := \frac{(3^{8-1-6})}{(4 \times (5 \times (7 - (9 - 20))))} := \frac{(3 + ((8 + 1) \times 6))}{((45 - 7) \times (9 \times 20))} := \frac{(3 + (8 - (1 \times 6)))}{((4 + ((5 \times 7) - 9)) \times 20)} \\ & := \frac{(3 + (8 \times (1 \times 6)))}{(((45 \times 7) - 9) \times 20)} := \frac{(3 + (8 + (1^6)))}{((4 + (5 + (7 \times 9))) \times 20)} := \frac{(3 + (8 + (1 + 6)))}{((45 + (7 \times 9)) \times 20)} := \frac{(3 + (8 + (1 - 6)))}{(4 \times (5 \times (7 + (9 + 20))))} \\ & := \frac{(3 + (81 - 6))}{((45 + 7) \times (9 \times 20))} := \frac{(38 - (1 \times 6))}{(4 \times ((57 - 9) \times 20))} := \frac{(38 + (1 \times 6))}{(4 \times ((57 + 9) \times 20))} := \frac{(38 + 16)}{(((45 \times 7) + 9) \times 20)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4023}{156897} & := \frac{((4 - (0 - 2)) \times 3)}{(1 + (5 + (689 + 7)))} := \frac{((4 \times (0 + 2))^3)}{(156 \times (8 \times (9 + 7)))} := \frac{((4^{02}) - 3)}{(15 + (6 \times (89 - 7)))} := \frac{((4 + (0 - 2))^3)}{((1 + 5) \times (68 - (9 + 7)))} \\ & := \frac{(4 - ((0 \times 2) - 3))}{(1 \times ((56 - (8 + 9)) \times 7))} := \frac{(4 - (0 - (2 \times 3)))}{(1 + (5 + (6 \times (8^9-7))))} := \frac{(4 - (0 - (2^3)))}{(1 \times ((5 \times (6 + 89)) - 7))} := \frac{(4 - (0 - (2 + 3)))}{(1 + (5 \times (6 + (8^9-7))))} \\ & := \frac{(4 - (0 - (2 - 3)))}{(1 + (5 + (6 + (8 + 97))))} := \frac{(4 - (0 - 23))}{(156 + 897)} := \frac{(4 \times (0 + (2 \times 3)))}{(156 \times (8 - (9 - 7)))} := \frac{(4 \times (0 + (2 + 3)))}{((1 + (5 + 6)) \times ((8 \times 9) - 7))} \\ & := \frac{(4^{0 \times 2+3})}{(156 \times (8 \times (9 - 7)))} := \frac{(4 + ((0 \times 2) - 3))}{(1 + ((5 + (6 + 8)) \times (9 - 7)))} := \frac{(4 + (0 - (2 - 3)))}{(1 + (((5 + 6) \times (8 + 9)) + 7))} := \frac{(40 - (2 + 3))}{(1 \times (5 \times (((6 \times 8) - 9) \times 7)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(40 + (2 \times 3))}{((1 - (5 - 6)) \times 897)} := \frac{(40 + (2 - 3))}{((1 + ((5 \times 6) + 8))^{9-7})} := \frac{(40 + 23)}{((1 + ((5 \times 6) + 8)) \times (9 \times 7))} := \frac{(402 - 3)}{(1 \times ((5^6) - (8^{9-7}))}$$

► **4653**
279180

$$:= \frac{((4 + (6 - 5)) \times 3)}{(((2 \times 7) - 9) \times 180)} := \frac{((4 + 6) \times (5 - 3))}{(((2^7) \times (9 + 1)) - 80)} := \frac{(4 - ((6 - 5) \times 3))}{((2 \times (7 \times (9 + 1))) - 80)} := \frac{(4 - ((6 - 5)^3))}{(2 + (7 - (9 - 180)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 - (6 - (5 + 3)))}{(279 + (1 + 80))} := \frac{(4 \times ((6 \times 5) - 3))}{((2 + (79 \times 1)) \times 80)} := \frac{(4 \times ((6 + 5) \times 3))}{(2 + (7918 - 0))} := \frac{(4 \times (6 - (5 - 3)))}{(((2^7) - (9 - 1)) \times (8 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 \times (6 \times (5 \times 3)))}{(27 \times ((9 + 1) \times 80))} := \frac{(4 \times (6 \times (5 + 3)))}{((2^7) \times (9 + (1 + 80)))} := \frac{(4 \times (6 \times (5 - 3)))}{((27 + (9 \times 1)) \times 80)} := \frac{(4 \times (6 + (5 - 3)))}{(((2 \times 7) + (9 + 1)) \times 80)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4^{(6-5)^3})}{((2 - (7 - (9 - 1))) \times 80)} := \frac{(4 + ((6 - 5)^3))}{(2 \times ((7 \times (9 + 1)) + 80))} := \frac{(4 + (6 - (5 + 3)))}{((2 \times (7 \times (9 - 1))) + (8 - 0))} := \frac{(4 + (6 - (5 - 3)))}{(((2 \times 7) - (9 - 1)) \times 80)}$$

$$:= \frac{(4 + (6^{5-3}))}{(2 \times ((7 + (9 - 1)) \times 80))} := \frac{(4 + (6 + (5 - 3)))}{(2 + (7 - (9 \times (1 - 80))))} := \frac{(46 - (5 - 3))}{(((2 \times (7 + 9)) + 1) \times 80)} := \frac{(46 + (5 + 3))}{((2 + (7 + 9)) \times 180)}$$

► **5328**
170496

$$:= \frac{(((5 + 3)^2) + 8)}{((1 - 7) \times (0 - (4 \times 96)))} := \frac{(((5 - (3 - 2))^8)}{((1 + (7 - 0))^{4+9-6})} := \frac{((5 \times (3 + 2)) + 8)}{(1 \times ((7 - (0 - 4)) \times 96))} := \frac{((5 \times 3) - (2 - 8))}{(1 \times (7 \times ((0 \times 4) + 96)))}$$

$$:= \frac{((5 \times 3) + (2 - 8))}{(1 - (7 + (0 - (49 \times 6))))} := \frac{((5^3) - (2 - 8))}{(((1 + (7 - 0))^4) + 96)} := \frac{((5 + 3) \times (2 \times 8))}{(((17 + (0 - (4 + 9)))^6)} := \frac{(5 - ((3 \times 2) - 8))}{(1 + (7 - (0 - (4 \times (9 \times 6))))))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - ((3^2) - 8))}{(1 \times (70 + (4 + (9 \times 6))))} := \frac{(5 - (3 - (2 + 8)))}{((1 + (7 + (0 - 4))) \times 96)} := \frac{(5 - (3 \times (2 - 8)))}{((1 + 7) \times (0 - (4 - 96)))} := \frac{(5 + ((3 \times 2) + 8))}{(1 \times (704 - 96))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + ((3 \times 2) - 8))}{((1^{704}) \times 96)} := \frac{(5 + (3 - (2 - 8)))}{(1 \times (7 \times (0 + (4^{9-6}))))} := \frac{(5 + (3 + (2 \times 8)))}{((1 + (7 - (0 \times 4))) \times 96)} := \frac{(5 + (3 + (2 + 8)))}{((1 - 7) \times ((0 \times 4) - 96))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (3 + (2 - 8)))}{(1 \times ((7 - (0 - (4 - 9)))^6))} := \frac{(5 + (3 + 28))}{((1 + (7 - (0 - 4))) \times 96)} := \frac{(53 + (2 + 8))}{((17 - (0 - 4)) \times 96)} := \frac{(53 - 28)}{(1 \times (704 + 96))}$$

► **5796**
231840

$$:= \frac{(((5 \times 7) + 9) \times 6)}{((2 + 31) \times (8 \times 40))} := \frac{((5 - (7 - 9)) \times 6)}{(2 \times ((3 + 18) \times 40))} := \frac{((5 \times 7) - (9 - 6))}{((2 + 318) \times (4 - 0))} := \frac{((5 + (7 + 9)) \times 6)}{(2 \times (3 \times (1 \times 840)))}$$

$$:= \frac{((5 + (7 - 9)) \times 6)}{((2 + ((3 - 1) \times 8)) \times 40)} := \frac{((5 + 79) \times 6)}{((23 + 1) \times 840)} := \frac{(5 - ((7 - 9) \times 6))}{((2 - (3 - 18)) \times 40)} := \frac{(5 - (7 - (9 + 6)))}{((2 + (3 + (1 \times 8))) \times 40)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - (7 - (9 - 6)))}{(2 - (3 - ((1^8) + 40)))} := \frac{(5 \times (7 - (9 - 6)))}{(2 \times ((3 - (1 - 8)) \times 40))} := \frac{(5 \times (7 \times (9 - 6)))}{((2 + (3 \times 1)) \times 840)} := \frac{(5 + (7 - (9 - 6)))}{(2 + (318 + 40))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (7 \times (9 - 6)))}{((2 + (3 \times (1 \times 8))) \times 40)} := \frac{(5 + (7 + (9 - 6)))}{((23 - (1 \times 8)) \times 40)} := \frac{(5 + (7 + 96))}{(2 \times (3 \times (18 \times 40)))} := \frac{(5 + (79 + 6))}{((2 + 3) \times (18 \times 40))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (79 - 6))}{(2 \times ((31 + 8) \times 40))} := \frac{(57 - (9 \times 6))}{((23 - (1 - 8)) \times (4 - 0))} := \frac{(57 - (9 - 6))}{(2 \times (3 \times ((1 + 8) \times 40)))} := \frac{(57 + (9 + 6))}{((2^3) \times ((1 + 8) \times 40))}$$

► **5917**
260348

$$:= \frac{(((5 \times 9) - 1)^7)}{((2 - (6 \times (0 - (3 + 4))))^8)} := \frac{((5 \times 9) + (1^7))}{((260 - (3 + 4)) \times 8)} := \frac{((5 \times 9) + (1 - 7))}{(((2 \times (6 - 0))^3) - (4 + 8))} := \frac{((5 \times 9) + 17)}{((260 + (3^4)) \times 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 \times 9) - 17}{(((2 \times 60) + 34) \times 8)} := \frac{((5 - 9) \times (1 - 7))}{(((2 \times 60) + (3 \times 4)) \times 8)} := \frac{(5 - (9 - (1 \times 7)))}{((2 + (6 - (0 - 3))) \times (4 + 8))} := \frac{(5 - (9 - (1 + 7)))}{(2 + (6 \times (0 - (3 - (4 \times 8))))))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 - (9 + (1 - 7)))}{((2 \times (6 - (0 - 34))) + 8)} := \frac{(5 \times (9 - (1 \times 7)))}{(2 - (6 \times (0 - ((3^4) - 8))))} := \frac{(5 \times (9 - (1^7)))}{(((2 \times (6 - 0))^3) + (4 \times 8))} := \frac{(5 \times (9 + (1 \times 7)))}{(2 \times (((6^{03}) + 4) \times 8))}$$

$$:= \frac{(5^{9-1-7})}{((2 - (60 - 3)) \times (4 - 8))} := \frac{(5 + (9 - (1 \times 7)))}{(2 - (6 \times (0 - (3 + 48))))} := \frac{(5 + (9 - (1 + 7)))}{(((2^{6+0 \times 3}) \times 4) + 8)} := \frac{(5 + (9 - (1 - 7)))}{(((2 + (6^{03})) \times 4) + 8)}$$

$$:= \frac{(5 + (9 \times (1^7)))}{((2 - (6 + (0 - (3^4)))) \times 8)} := \frac{(5 + (9 + (1^7)))}{((2 \times (6 - 0)) + ((3^4) \times 8))} := \frac{(5 + (9 + (1 + 7)))}{(((2 \times 60) - (3 - 4)) \times 8)} := \frac{(5 + (9 + (1 - 7)))}{((2 - (6 \times (0 - (3 + 4)))) \times 8)}$$

► **6234**
105978

$$:= \frac{((6 \times (2 \times 3)) + 4)}{(((105 - 9) \times 7) + 8)} := \frac{((6 \times (2 \times 3)) - 4)}{(1 \times (0 + ((5 + (9 \times 7)) \times 8)))} := \frac{((6 \times 2) + (3 + 4))}{(1 \times (0 + ((5 \times (9 \times 7)) + 8)))} := \frac{((6 \times 2) + 34)}{(1 - (0 - (5 + (97 \times 8))))}$$

$$:= \frac{((6^2) - (3 + 4))}{(1 \times (0 + ((5 \times 97) + 8)))} := \frac{((6 + (2 \times 3)) \times 4)}{(1 \times (0 + ((5 + 97) \times 8)))} := \frac{((62 \times 3) + 4)}{(10 \times ((5 \times (9 \times 7)) + 8))} := \frac{(6 - ((2^3) - 4))}{(1 - (0 - ((5^{9-7}) + 8)))}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(6 - (2 - (3 \times 4)))}{(((10 \times 5) - (9 + 7)) \times 8)} := \frac{(6 - (2 - (3 - 4)))}{(1 - (0 - (5 \times (9 - (7 - 8)))))} := \frac{(6 - (2 \times (3 - 4)))}{((10^5) + (9 \times (7 + 8)))} := \frac{(6 - (2 + (3 - 4)))}{(1 + (0 - (5 - (97 - 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 - (2 - 34))}{((10 \times 59) + (7 \times 8))} := \frac{(6 \times (2 - (3 - 4)))}{((10 \times 5) + ((9 - 7)^8))} := \frac{(6^{2+3-4})}{(1 - (0 - ((5 \times 9) + (7 \times 8))))} := \frac{(6 + ((2^3) - 4))}{(10 \times ((5^{9-7}) - 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 + (2 - (3 + 4)))}{(1 \times (0 + ((5^{9-7}) - 8)))} := \frac{(6 + (2 \times (3 \times 4)))}{(1 - (0 - (5 + (9 \times (7 \times 8)))))} := \frac{(6 + (2 \times (3 - 4)))}{(10 + (59 + (7 - 8)))} := \frac{(6 + (2 + (3 - 4)))}{((10 \times 5) - (9 - 78))}
 \end{aligned}$$

▶ $\frac{8267}{140539}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((8 + 2) \times 6) + 7)}{(14 - (0 - ((5^3) \times 9)))} := \frac{((8 \times (2 + 6)) + 7)}{(1 + ((405 \times 3) - 9))} := \frac{((8 \times 2) - (6 - 7))}{(1 - (4 \times (0 - ((5 + 3) \times 9))))} := \frac{((8 \times 2) + (6 \times 7))}{(1 + ((40^5) - 39))} \\
 &:= \frac{((8 + (2 \times 6)) \times 7)}{(140 \times (5 + (3 + 9)))} := \frac{((8 + (2 - 6)) \times 7)}{(14 \times (0 - (5 - 39)))} := \frac{((8 - 2) \times (6 + 7))}{((1 - 40) \times (5 - 39))} := \frac{(8 - ((2 \times 6) - 7))}{(1 \times ((4 \times (0 + (5 \times 3))) - 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 - ((2 - 6) \times 7))}{(((1 + (40 \times 5)) \times 3) + 9)} := \frac{(8 - (2 - (6 - 7)))}{(1 + (40 + (5 + 39)))} := \frac{(8 - (2 \times (6 - 7)))}{(140 - (5 \times (3 - 9)))} := \frac{(8 \times ((2 \times 6) - 7))}{(1 \times (40 \times (5 + (3 + 9))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 \times (2 + 67))}{(((1 + (4 - 0))^5 \times 3) + 9)} := \frac{(8^{2+6-7})}{(1 \times (4 \times (0 - (5 - 39))))} := \frac{(8 + ((2 \times 6) - 7))}{(1 \times ((4 \times (0 + 53)) + 9))} := \frac{(8 + (2 - (6 - 7)))}{((14^{05-3}) - 9)} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 + (2 \times (6 - 7)))}{(1 \times (40 + (53 + 9)))} := \frac{(8 + (2 + (6 - 7)))}{((1 + (4^{05-3})) \times 9)} := \frac{(8 + (26 + 7))}{((1 + 40) \times (5 + (3 + 9)))} := \frac{(82 - (6 - 7))}{(1405 - (3 - 9))}
 \end{aligned}$$

▶ $\frac{8946}{107352}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((8 - (9 - 4)) \times 6)}{((1 - (0 - 7)) \times (3^{5-2}))} := \frac{((8 \times (9 - 4)) + 6)}{(((107 + 3) \times 5) + 2)} := \frac{((8 \times 9) - (4 \times 6))}{((10 - (7 \times (3 - 5)))^2)} := \frac{((8 \times 9) + (4 - 6))}{(10 \times ((7 + 35) \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{((8 - 9) \times (4 - 6))}{(1 + (0 - (7 - (3 \times (5 \times 2)))))} := \frac{(8 - (9 - (4 + 6)))}{(1 - (0 - ((7 \times (3 \times 5)) + 2)))} := \frac{(8 - (9 \times (4 - 6)))}{((10 - (7 - 3)) \times 52)} := \frac{(8 - (9 + (4 - 6)))}{(1 - (0 - (7 - (3 - (5 + 2)))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 - (9 - 46))}{(10 \times ((7 \times (3 + 5)) - 2))} := \frac{(8 \times ((9^4) \times 6))}{(((1 - (0 - 7)) \times (3^5))^2)} := \frac{(8 \times (9 - (4 - 6)))}{((10 - 7) \times 352)} := \frac{(8 + ((9 \times 4) + 6))}{((1 - (0 - 7)) \times (3 \times (5^2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 + ((9 + 4) \times 6))}{((1 - (0 - (7^3))) \times (5 - 2))} := \frac{(8 + (9 - (4 + 6)))}{(1 \times (0 + ((7 + 35) \times 2)))} := \frac{(8 + (9 - (4 - 6)))}{(10 - (7 - ((3 \times 5)^2)))} := \frac{(8 + (9 + (4 \times 6)))}{((1 - (0 - (7 \times 35))) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 + (9 + (4 + 6)))}{((10 - (7 - (3 \times 5)))^2)} := \frac{(8 + (9 + (4 - 6)))}{(10 \times ((7 - (3 - 5)) \times 2))} := \frac{(8 + (94 + 6))}{(((10^7) + 35)^2)} := \frac{(89 - (4 - 6))}{(1 \times (0 + (7 \times (3 \times 52))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

▶ $\frac{9603}{172854}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((9 \times (6 - 0)) + 3)}{(172 + 854)} := \frac{((9 \times (6 - 0)) - 3)}{(1 \times ((7 + (2 + 8)) \times 54))} := \frac{((9 + (6 - 0)) \times 3)}{((1 + (7 + 2)) \times (85 - 4))} := \frac{(9 - (6 - (0 \times 3)))}{(1 - (7 + (2 - (8 + 54))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 - (6 \times (0 \times 3)))}{(1 - (7 - ((2 + (8 \times 5)) \times 4)))} := \frac{(9 - (6 + (0 - 3)))}{((1 - (7 - (28 + 5))) \times 4)} := \frac{(9 \times (6 - (0 \times 3)))}{((1 + (7 + (2 + 8))) \times 54)} := \frac{(9 \times (6 - (0 - 3)))}{((17 + (2 + 8)) \times 54)} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 \times (6 \times (0 + 3)))}{(((1 + 72) \times (8 \times 5)) - 4)} := \frac{(9 \times (6 + (0 - 3)))}{(((17^2) + 8) \times 54)} := \frac{(9 + (6 - (0 \times 3)))}{(1 - (7 - ((2^8) + (5 \times 4))))} := \frac{(9 + (6 - (0 - 3)))}{((1 - (7 - (2 + 85))) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 + (6^{03}))}{((1 + (7^2)) \times (85 - 4))} := \frac{(9 + (6 + (0 - 3)))}{(1 \times ((7 \times 28) + (5 \times 4)))} := \frac{(9 + (60 + 3))}{(1 \times ((7 + (2 - (8 - 5)))^4))} := \frac{(9 + (60 - 3))}{((1 - (7 - 28)) \times 54)} \\
 &:= \frac{(96 - (0 \times 3))}{(1728 \times (5 - 4))} := \frac{(96 - (0 - 3))}{((17 + (2 \times 8)) \times 54)} := \frac{(96 \times (0 + 3))}{(1 \times (72 \times (8 \times (5 + 4))))} := \frac{(96 + (0 - 3))}{(1728 - 54)}
 \end{aligned}$$

▶ $\frac{9804}{137256}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((9 - (8 - 0)) \times 4)}{(1 \times (3 - (7 - (2 \times (5 \times 6)))))} := \frac{((9 \times (8 - 0)) + 4)}{(1 \times (((3 \times 7) - 2) \times 56))} := \frac{((9 + (8 - 0)) \times 4)}{(1 \times ((3 + (7 \times 2)) \times 56))} := \frac{((9 + 80) \times 4)}{(((13 \times 7) - 2) \times 56)} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 - (8 - (0 \times 4)))}{(1 + (3 + (7 + (2 - (5 - 6)))))} := \frac{(9 - (8 \times (0 \times 4)))}{(1 \times ((3 - (7 - 25)) \times 6))} := \frac{(9 - (8 + (0 - 4)))}{(1 \times (3 + (7 + (2 \times (5 \times 6)))))} := \frac{(9 \times (8 - (0 \times 4)))}{((1 + (3 + (7 \times 2))) \times 56)} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 \times (8 - (0 - 4)))}{(1 \times (3 \times ((7 + 2) \times 56)))} := \frac{(9 \times (8 \times (0 + 4)))}{(1 \times (3 \times (7 \times ((2^5) \times 6))))} := \frac{(9 \times (8 + (0 - 4)))}{((1 + (3 + (7 - 2))) \times 56)} := \frac{(9^{8-04})}{(1 \times ((3^7) \times ((2 + 5) \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 + (8 - (0 \times 4)))}{(1 + (3 + ((7 + (2^5)) \times 6)))} := \frac{(9 + (8 - (0 - 4)))}{((1 + (3 + ((7 + 2) \times 5))) \times 6)} := \frac{(9 + (8 + (0 - 4)))}{(1 + (((37 - 2) \times 5) + 6))} := \frac{(9 + (80 - 4))}{(1 \times ((37 \times (2^5)) + 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(98 - (0 \times 4))}{((1 + 3) \times (7^{2-5+6}))} := \frac{(98 - (0 - 4))}{(1 \times (((37^2) - 5) \times 6))} := \frac{(98 + (0 - 4))}{(1372 - 56)} := \frac{(980 - 4)}{((1 + (3^{7-2})) \times 56)}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.20 21 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{16298}{57043} &:= \frac{(((1+6)^2) + (9+8))}{((57 \times (0+4)) + 3)} := \frac{((1^{62}) \times 98)}{((5 \times 70) - (4+3))} := \frac{((1+(6-2)) \times 98)}{(5 \times (7^{0 \times 4+3}))} \\ &:= \frac{((1+6) \times ((2 \times 9) - 8))}{(5 \times (7 \times (0+(4+3))))} := \frac{((1+6) \times (2+98))}{(5 \times (70 \times (4+3)))} := \frac{(1 - (6 - (29 - 8)))}{(57 + (0 - (4 - 3)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (((6 \times 2) - 9) \times 8))}{((5 + (7 - 0)) \times (4 + 3))} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 2 \times 9 - 8}{5 \times 70 \times (4 - 3)} := \frac{(1 \times ((6 \times (2 + 9)) - 8))}{(5 + ((70 - 4) \times 3))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times ((6 \times 2) + 98))}{(5 \times (70 + (4 + 3)))} := \frac{(1 \times (6 - (2 \times (9 - 8))))}{(5 + ((7 + (0 - 4)) \times 3))} := \frac{(1 \times (6 - (2 - 98)))}{((5 \times 70) + (4 + 3))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (6 \times (2 \times (9 - 8))))}{((5 \times (7 - 0)) + (4 + 3))} := \frac{(1 \times (6 \times (2 + (9 + 8))))}{(1 \times (6 \times (2 + (9 - 8))))} := \frac{(1 \times (6 \times (2 + (9 - 8))))}{(1 \times (6 \times (2 + (9 - 8))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (6 + (2 \times (9 \times 8))))}{((5 + 70) \times (4 + 3))} := \frac{(1 \times (6 + (2 \times (9 - 8))))}{((5 \times (7 - 0)) - (4 + 3))} := \frac{(1 + ((6 \times 2) + (9 + 8)))}{(5 \times (7 \times ((0 \times 4) + 3)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + ((6^2) - (9 + 8)))}{(5 \times (7 - (0 - (4 + 3))))} := \frac{(1 + (6 + (2 + (9 - 8))))}{(5 \times (7 - (0 \times 43)))} := \frac{(16 + (2 + (9 \times 8)))}{(5 \times (70 - (4 + 3)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{19076}{23845} &:= \frac{(1^9 + 07)^6}{(2^3 + 8)^4 \times 5} := \frac{((1 - (9 \times (0 - 7))) \times 6)}{((2^3) \times ((8 + 4) \times 5))} := \frac{1^9 \times 076}{23 + 8 \times (4 + 5)} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + (9 - (0 \times 7))) \times 6)}{((2 \times (3 + (8 \times 4))) + 5)} := \frac{((1 + (90 - 7)) \times 6)}{(((2 + 3)^{8-4}) + 5)} := \frac{((1 - 9) \times (0 - (7 \times 6)))}{(2 \times ((38 + 4) \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{((19 + (0 - 7)) \times 6)}{(((2 \times (3 + 8)) - 4) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 - (9 + (0 - 76)))}{((2 + (3 + (8 + 4))) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 \times ((9 - (0 - 7)) \times 6))}{(2 \times (3 \times ((8 - 4) \times 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times ((9 + (0 - 7)) \times 6))}{((2 - (3 - (8 - 4))) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 \times ((9 + (0 - 7))^6))}{(2 \times (3 - (8 - 45)))} := \frac{(1 \times (9 + (0 - (7 - 6))))}{(2 \times ((3 - 8) \times (4 - 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (90 - (7 \times 6)))}{(2 \times (3 + ((8 \times 4) - 5)))} := \frac{(1 \times (90 + (7 \times 6)))}{(1 + (9 + ((0 \times 7) - 6)))} := \frac{(1 + 9 - ((0 \times 7) - 6))}{(2 \times (3 + (8 + (4 - 5))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (9 - (0 - (7 \times 6))))}{(2 + (3 + ((8 + 4) \times 5)))} := \frac{(1 + (9 + ((0 \times 7) - 6)))}{(2 - (3 \times (8 - (4 + 5))))} := \frac{(1 + (90 + (7 + 6)))}{(((2 \times (3 + 8)) + 4) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(19 - (0 - (7 + 6)))}{(2 \times (3 + (8 + (4 + 5))))} := \frac{(19 - (0 - (7 - 6)))}{(2 + (3 + ((8 - 4) \times 5)))} := \frac{(190 - (7 \times 6))}{(2 + (3 + (8 \times 4))) \times 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{19530}{46872} &:= \frac{(((1^9) + 5) \times 30)}{((4 - (6 - 8)) \times 72)} := \frac{(((1^{95}) \times 30)}{(4 \times (6 \times (8 - (7 - 2))))} := \frac{((1 + (9 \times 5)) \times 30)}{(46 \times (8 \times (7 + 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + (9 - 5)) \times (3 - 0))}{(4 \times (6 + (8 - (7 - 2))))} := \frac{((1 + (9 - 5)) \times 30)}{((4 + 68) \times (7 - 2))} := \frac{((1 + 9) \times (5 - (3 - 0)))}{(4 \times (6 - (8 - (7 \times 2))))} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + 9)^{5-3} + 0)}{(4 \times (6 + ((8 \times 7) - 2)))} := \frac{((1 - 9) \times (5 - 30))}{(4 \times ((6 \times 8) + 72))} := \frac{((19 + 5) \times 30)}{(4 \times (6 \times (8 \times (7 + 2))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times ((9 + 5) \times 30))}{((4 + 68) \times (7 \times 2))} := \frac{(1 \times ((9 - 5) \times 30))}{(((4 \times 6) + 8) \times (7 + 2))} := \frac{(1 \times (9 \times (5 + 30)))}{((46 + 8) \times (7 \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (95 + 30))}{((4 + 6) \times ((8 + 7) \times 2))} := \frac{(1 \times (95 - 30))}{(4 \times ((6 \times 8) - (7 + 2)))} := \frac{(1 + (9 - (5 - 30)))}{((4 - (6 - 8)) \times (7 \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (9 + (5 \times 30)))}{(4 \times (((6 + 8) \times 7) - 2))} := \frac{1 + 9 + 5^3 + 0}{((4 - ((6 - 8) \times 7))^2)} := \frac{(1 + (9 + (5 + 30)))}{((4 - (6 - (8 \times 7))) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (9 + 530))}{(4 \times (6 \times ((8 \times 7) - 2)))} := \frac{195 + 30}{468 + 72} := \frac{195 - 30}{468 - 72} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20916}{78435} &:= \frac{((2 - (0 - (9 - 1))) \times 6)}{((7 + 8)^{4+3-5})} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + (9 \times 1))) + 6)}{(78 + (4 + (3 + 5)))} := \frac{((20 + 9) \times 16)}{(7 + (((8 + 4)^3) + 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((209 - 1) \times 6)}{(78 \times (4 \times (3 \times 5)))} := \frac{2 + 09 - 1 - 6}{7 + 8 \times (4 - 3)^5} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (9 \times (1 \times 6))))}{((7 - (8 - 43)) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (9 + (1^6))))}{((7 - (8 - 4)) \times (3 \times 5))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + ((9 + 1) \times 6)))}{(7 + (8 + 435))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (9 - (1^6))))}{((7 \times 8) - (4 - (3 + 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (9 - (1 - 6))))}{(7 \times (8 + ((4 \times 3) - 5)))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (9 \times (1 \times 6))))}{(((7 \times (8 + 4)) - 3) \times 5)} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (9 + (1^6))))}{(7 + (8 + (4 \times (3 \times 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (9 + (1 - 6))))}{(7 - (8 + (4 - 35)))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (91 \times 6)))}{(7 + ((8^4) - (3 + 5)))} := \frac{(2^{0 \times 91 + 6})}{((7 \times ((8 \times 4) + 3)) - 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2^{09+16})}{((7 + 8) \times (4 \times (3 + 5)))} := \frac{(20 \times (9 - (1^6)))}{(((7 \times 8) + (4^3)) \times 5)} := \frac{(20 \times (9 - (1 - 6)))}{(78 + (4 \times (3^5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(20 + ((9 - 1) \times 6))}{(7 - (8 \times (4 - 35)))} := \frac{(20 + (9 + (1 + 6)))}{((7 + (8 + (4 \times 3))) \times 5)} := \frac{(209 - (1^6))}{(((7 \times 8) - 4) \times (3 \times 5))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{58912}{73640} &:= \frac{(((5 \times (8 + 9)) - 1) \times 2)}{(7 \times (3 \times (6 + (4 - 0))))} := \frac{(((5 + 8) \times (9 + 1)) - 2)}{((7 + (3 - 6)) \times 40)} := \frac{(((5 + 8) \times 9) - (1^2))}{(7 + (3 \times (6 + 40)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 - (8 - (9 \times 1)))^2)}{((7 \times 3) + (6 \times (4 - 0)))} := \frac{((5 \times 8) - (9 - (1^2)))}{((7 - (3 - 6)) \times (4 - 0))} := \frac{((5 \times 8) - (9 + (1 + 2)))}{(7 \times (3 + (6 - (4 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 \times 8) + ((9 + 1) \times 2))}{(73 + (6 - (4 - 0)))} := \frac{((5 + (8 + (9 \times 1))) \times 2)}{((7 \times 3) - (6 - 40))} := \frac{((5 + (8 - 9)) \times 12)}{(((7 \times 3) - 6) \times (4 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 + 8) \times (9 - (1^2)))}{((7 \times (3 \times 6)) + (4 - 0))} := \frac{((58 \times (9 \times 1)) - 2)}{(7 + (3 + 640))} := \frac{(5 \times ((89 + 1)^2))}{(((7 \times 3) - 6)^4 + 0)} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times (8 \times ((9 + 1) \times 2)))}{((7 + (3 \times 6)) \times 40)} := \frac{(5 \times (8 \times (9 - (1^2))))}{((7 - (3 - 6)) \times 40)} := \frac{(5 \times (8 \times (9 + (1 + 2))))}{(((7 \times 3) - 6) \times 40)} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times (8 + (9 - (1^2))))}{((7 + (3 \times 6)) \times (4 - 0))} := \frac{(5 + (8 - (9 - 12)))}{(7 + (3 + (6 + (4 - 0))))} := \frac{(5 + (8 + (9 \times (1 + 2))))}{(7 - (3 - (6 + 40)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(58 - (9 - (1 + 2)))}{(7 + ((3 \times 6) + 40))} := \frac{(58 + (9 + (1^2)))}{((7 \times 3) + (64 - 0))} := \frac{(589 + (1 + 2))}{(7 + ((3^6) + (4 - 0)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{74610}{89532} &:= \frac{(((7 \times 4) + 6) \times 10)}{(8 \times ((9 \times 5) + (3 \times 2)))} := \frac{(((7 + 4) \times 6) - (1 - 0))}{(8 + ((9 \times (5 + 3)) - 2))} := \frac{((7 - (4 - 6)) \times 10)}{(8 + (95 + (3 + 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 \times (4 + 6)) + 10)}{(8 - ((9 - 53) \times 2))} := \frac{((7 \times (4 + 6)) - 10)}{(8 \times (9 - (5 - (3 + 2))))} := \frac{((7^4) - (61 - 0))}{(8 - (9 - (53^2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 + (4 + 6)) \times 10)}{(8 + ((95 + 3) \times 2))} := \frac{((7 + (4 - 6)) \times 10)}{((8 + (9 - 5)) \times (3 + 2))} := \frac{((7 + 4) \times (6 - (1 - 0)))}{(((8 - (9 - 5))^3) + 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 + 4) \times (6 \times 10))}{(8 \times (9 \times (5 + (3 \times 2))))} := \frac{((7 - 4) \times (6 \times 10))}{(89 + ((5^3) + 2))} := \frac{((74 \times 6) + (1 - 0))}{(89 \times (5 + (3 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 - (4 - (6 + (1 - 0))))}{(8 + (9 - (5 \times (3 - 2))))} := \frac{(7 \times (4 + (6 \times (1 - 0))))}{(7 \times (4 + (6 \times (1 - 0))))} := \frac{(7 + ((4 \times 6) - (1 - 0)))}{(7 + ((4 \times 6) - (1 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (4 - (6 \times (1 - 0))))}{(8 + (9 - (5 \times (3 - 2))))} := \frac{(89 - (5 \times (3 - 2)))}{(7 + (4 - (6 - 10)))} := \frac{(8 - (9 - (5 + 32)))}{(7 + (4 \times (6 + (1 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 + (9 - (5 + (3 \times 2))))}{(74 \times (6 - (1 - 0)))} := \frac{(8 + (9 - (5 - (3 \times 2))))}{(74 + (61 - 0))} := \frac{(8 + (9 + (5 \times (3 + 2))))}{(746 - (1 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(89 \times 5) - (3 - 2)}{((89 \times 5) - (3 - 2))} := \frac{(89 - (5 + 3)) \times 2}{((89 - (5 + 3)) \times 2)} := \frac{(895 - (3 - 2))}{(895 - (3 - 2))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{75249}{83610} := \frac{(((7 - (5 - 2))^4) \times 9)}{((8^3) \times (6 - (1 - 0)))} := \frac{(((7 \times (5 \times 2)) - 4) \times 9)}{((8 + 3) \times (6 \times 10))} := \frac{(((7 \times 5) - 24) \times 9)}{((8 - (3 - 6)) \times 10)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{((7 - (5 - (2^4))) \times 9)}{(((8 \times 3) - 6) \times 10)} & := \frac{((7 - (5 - (2 + 4))) \times 9)}{(8 \times (3 + (6 + (1 - 0))))} & := \frac{((7 - (5 \times (2 - 4))) \times 9)}{((8 + (3 + 6)) \times 10)} \\
 & := \frac{((7 - (5 - 24)) \times 9)}{(8 + (3 \times 6)) \times 10} & := \frac{((7 + (5 + (2^4))) \times 9)}{(8 \times (36 - (1 - 0)))} & := \frac{((7 + 5) \times ((2 + 4) \times 9))}{(8 \times ((3 + 6) \times 10))} \\
 & := \frac{((7 + 5) \times (24 \times 9))}{(8 \times (36 \times 10))} & := \frac{((7 + 5) \times (24 + 9))}{((8 + 36) \times 10)} & := \frac{(7 - ((5^2) - (4 \times 9)))}{(8 - (3 \times (6 - 10)))} \\
 & := \frac{(7 - (5 - (2 - (4 - 9))))}{(8 - (3 - (6 - (1 - 0))))} & := \frac{(7 - (5 + (2 - (4 \times 9))))}{(((8 - 3) \times 6) + 10)} & := \frac{(7 \times ((5 + (2 + 4)) \times 9))}{((83 - 6) \times 10)} \\
 & := \frac{(7 + ((5^2) + 49))}{(83 + (6 + (1 - 0)))} & := \frac{(7 + (5 + (2 + (4 + 9))))}{((8 - 3) \times (6 \times (1 - 0)))} & := \frac{(7 + (5 + (24 + 9)))}{((8 + (3 - 6)) \times 10)} \\
 & := \frac{(7 + (52 + 49))}{(8 \times (3 \times (6 - (1 - 0))))} & := \frac{(7 + 5249)}{(8 \times ((3^6) + (1 - 0)))} & := \frac{(752 + 49)}{((83 + 6) \times 10)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{4591}{367280}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(((4 + 5) \times 9) - 1)}{(((3 \times 6) + 7) \times (2^8 + 0))} & := \frac{((4 \times (5 + 9)) + 1)}{((3 + (6 \times (7 + 2))) \times 80)} & := \frac{((4 \times 5) - (9 \times 1))}{((3 - (6 - (7 \times 2))) \times 80)} \\
 & := \frac{((4 \times 5) - (9 + 1))}{((3^6) - (7 + (2 - 80)))} & := \frac{((4 \times 5) - (9 - 1))}{(3 \times (((6 \times 7) - 2) \times (8 - 0)))} & := \frac{((4 \times 5) + (9 \times 1))}{((3 + ((6 + 7) \times 2)) \times 80)} \\
 & := \frac{((4 + 5) \times (9 \times 1))}{((3 + (6 + 72)) \times 80)} & := \frac{((4 + 5) \times (9 - 1))}{((3 + (67 + 2)) \times 80)} & := \frac{((4 + 5) \times 91)}{(3 + 6) \times 7280} \\
 & := \frac{((4 + 5)^9 \times 1)}{(((3 + 6)^{7+2}) \times 80)} & := \frac{(4 - (5 - (9 \times 1)))}{((3 - (6 - 7)) \times (2 \times 80))} & := \frac{(4 - (5 - (9 + 1)))}{(3 \times (6 \times ((7 - 2) \times (8 - 0))))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 - (5 - (9 - 1)))}{((3 + (6 - 7)) \times 280)} & := \frac{(4 - (5 - 91))}{(3 \times (6 \times ((7 - 2) \times 80)))} & := \frac{(4 \times (5 \times (9 \times 1)))}{(36 \times ((7 - 2) \times 80))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times (5 + (9 \times 1)))}{((3 + (6 + 7)) \times 280)} & := \frac{(4 \times (5 + (9 + 1)))}{(3 \times ((6 + (7 \times 2)) \times 80))} & := \frac{(4 + ((5 \times 9) + 1))}{((36 + (7 \times 2)) \times 80)} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + (5 - (9 - 1)))}{(3 + (6 - (7 + (2 - 80))))} & := \frac{(4 + (5 + (9 \times 1)))}{(3 \times (6 \times (72 + (8 - 0))))} & := \frac{(45 - (9 \times 1))}{(36 \times (72 + (8 - 0)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{5304}{169728}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{((5 - (3 - 0))^4)}{(1 \times ((6 + (9 + (7^2))) \times 8))} & := \frac{((5 \times (3 - 0)) + 4)}{((1 - (6 - (9 + 72))) \times 8)} & := \frac{((5 \times (3 - 0)) - 4)}{(1 \times ((6 + (9 + 7)) \times (2 \times 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{((5 \times 30) + 4)}{((169 + 7) \times 28)} & := \frac{((5 \times 30) - 4)}{(1 \times (((6 \times 97) + 2) \times 8))} & := \frac{((5^3 + 0) + 4)}{(16 \times (9 - (7 - (2^8))))} \\
 & := \frac{((5^3 + 0) - 4)}{(1 \times (((6 + (9 + 7))^2) \times 8))} & := \frac{((5 + (3 - 0)) \times 4)}{(1 \times ((6 - (9 - 7)) \times (2^8)))} & := \frac{((5 + 30) \times 4)}{((1 + 69) \times (72 - 8))} \\
 & := \frac{(5 - (3 - (0 \times 4)))}{(1 - (6 - (97 - 28)))} & := \frac{(5 - (3 \times (0 \times 4)))}{(1 + (6 + (9 \times (7 + (2 + 8)))))} & := \frac{(5 - (3 \times (0 - 4)))}{((1 + (6 + ((9 \times 7) - 2))) \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{(5 - (3 + (0 - 4)))}{(1 \times (6 \times (9 + (7 + (2 \times 8)))))} & := \frac{(5 \times (3 - (0 \times 4)))}{((1 - (6 - ((9 \times 7) + 2))) \times 8)} & := \frac{(5 \times (3 - (0 - 4)))}{((1 + (6 + (9 \times 7))) \times (2 \times 8))} \\
 & := \frac{(5 + (3 - (0 \times 4)))}{(1 \times ((6 - (9 - (7 - 2)))^8))} & := \frac{(5 + (3 - (0 - 4)))}{(1 \times (6 - (9 \times (7 \times (2 - 8)))))} & := \frac{(5 + (3 + (0 - 4)))}{(1 + (6 + (9 + (7 \times (2 \times 8)))))} \\
 & := \frac{(5 + (30 - 4))}{(1 \times ((69 - 7) \times (2 \times 8)))} & := \frac{(53 - (0 \times 4))}{((1 + ((6 + 9) \times 7)) \times (2 \times 8))} & := \frac{(53 + (0 - 4))}{((1 - (6 - 9)) \times ((7^2) \times 8))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{5769}{103842}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{((5 \times (7 + 6)) - 9)}{(1 \times (0 + (3 \times (8 \times 42))))} & := \frac{((5 \times 7) + (6 - 9))}{(((1 + (0 - (3 - 8))) \times 4)^2)} & := \frac{((5 \times 7) + 69)}{((10 + 3) \times ((8 + 4)^2))} \\
 & := \frac{((5 + (7 + 6)) \times 9)}{((10 + ((3 + 8) \times 4))^2)} & := \frac{((5 + 7) \times (6 \times 9))}{(((10 + 3) \times 8) + 4)^2} & := \frac{((5 + 76) \times 9)}{(1 \times (0 + ((3^8) \times (4 - 2))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(5 - ((7 - 6)^9))}{(1 \times (0 + (3 \times (8 + (4^2)))))} & := \frac{(5 - (7 - (6 \times 9)))}{((10^3) - (8^4 - 2))} & := \frac{(5 - (7 - (6 + 9)))}{((1 - (0 - 38)) \times (4 + 2))} \\
 & := \frac{(5 - (7 + (6 - 9)))}{(1 \times (0 + (3 \times (8 - (4 - 2)))))} & := \frac{(5 \times (7 - (6 - 9)))}{((1 + (0 - (3 - (8 \times 4))))^2)} & := \frac{(5 \times (7 + (6 - 9)))}{(10 \times (38 - (4 - 2)))} \\
 & := \frac{(5^{(7-6)^9})}{(1 - (0 - (3 + (84 + 2))))} & := \frac{(5 + ((7 - 6) \times 9))}{((1 + (0 - (3 - 8))) \times 42)} & := \frac{(5 + ((7 - 6)^9))}{(10 + ((3 \times (8 \times 4)) + 2))} \\
 & := \frac{(5 + (7 - (6 - 9)))}{(10 \times (3 + (8 + (4^2))))} & := \frac{(5 + (7 + (6 - 9)))}{(1 \times (0 - ((3 - 84) \times 2)))} & := \frac{(5 + (76 + 9))}{(10 \times ((3^{8-4}) \times 2))} \\
 & := \frac{(5 + (76 - 9))}{(1 \times (0 + ((3 \times (8 + 4))^2)))} & := \frac{(57 - (6 \times 9))}{(1 - (0 - (3 + (8 + 42))))} & := \frac{(57 - (6 - 9))}{(1038 + 42)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{6057}{193824}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{((6 - (0 - 5)) \times 7)}{(1 - (9 - (3 \times 824)))} & := \frac{((6 \times (0 + 5)) - 7)}{((1 - (9 - (3 \times (8^2)))) \times 4)} & := \frac{((6 + (0 - 5)) \times 7)}{(1 \times ((9 - (3 - 8)) \times (2^4)))} \\
 & := \frac{((6 + (0 - 5))^7)}{(1 - ((9 \times (3 - (8 - 2))) - 4))} & := \frac{(6 - ((0 \times 5) - 7))}{((1 + (93 + (8 + 2))) \times 4)} & := \frac{(6 - (0 - (5 \times 7)))}{(19 - (3 - ((8 - 2)^4)))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 - (0 - (5 + 7)))}{(1 \times ((9 + 3) \times (8 \times (2 + 4))))} & := \frac{(6 - (0 - (5 - 7)))}{((1 - (9 - (38 + 2))) \times 4)} & := \frac{(6 - (0 \times 57))}{(1 \times (((9 - (3 - 8))^2) - 4))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 \times ((0 \times 5) + 7))}{((1 + (9 - 3)) \times (8 \times 24))} & := \frac{(6 \times (0 - (5 - 7)))}{((1 + (9 + 38)) \times (2 \times 4))} & := \frac{(6 \times (0 + (5 + 7)))}{(1 \times ((9 + 3) \times (8 \times 24)))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 \times (0 + 57))}{(19 \times (3 \times (8 \times 24)))} & := \frac{(6^{-05+7})}{((1 + (9 + 38)) \times 24)} & := \frac{(6 + (0 - (5 - 7)))}{((1 - (9 \times (3 - (8 + 2)))) \times 4)} \\
 & := \frac{(60 - (5 \times 7))}{((1 + (9 \times (3 + 8))) \times (2 \times 4))} & := \frac{(60 - (5 + 7))}{(1 \times ((9 - 3) \times ((8^2) \times 4)))} & := \frac{(60 \times (5 + 7))}{((1 + 9) \times (((3 \times 8)^2) \times 4))} \\
 & := \frac{(60 + (5 \times 7))}{(19 \times ((38 + 2) \times 4))} & := \frac{(60 + 57)}{(1 \times ((938 - 2) \times 4))} & := \frac{(60 - 57)}{(1 \times ((9 + (3 - 8)) \times 24))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{9153}{207468}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{((9 - (1 - 5)) \times 3)}{((2 - (0 - (7 + 4))) \times 68)} & := \frac{((9 \times (1 \times 5)) + 3)}{(2 \times (0 + ((74 - 6) \times 8)))} & := \frac{((9 \times (1 + 5)) - 3)}{((20 - (7 - 4)) \times 68)} \\
 & := \frac{((9 \times (1 + 5)) \times 3)}{(((20 + 7)^4) \times 68)} & := \frac{((9 + (1^5)) \times 3)}{(((2 \times (0 + 7)) - 4) \times 68)} & := \frac{((9 + (1 + 5)) \times 3)}{(20 \times (7 - (4 - (6 \times 8))))} \\
 & := \frac{((9 + (1 - 5)) \times 3)}{((2 - (0 - (7 - 4))) \times 68)} & := \frac{((9 - 1) \times (5 \times 3))}{(20 \times ((7 + (4 + 6)) \times 8))} & := \frac{((91 + 5) \times 3)}{(((20 \times 7) - 4) \times (6 \times 8))} \\
 & := \frac{((91 - 5) \times 3)}{((2 - (0 - ((7 - 4)^6))) \times 8)} & := \frac{(9 - (1 + (5 - 3)))}{(2 \times ((0 \times 74) + 68))} & := \frac{(9 \times ((1^5) + 3))}{((20 - (7 - 4)) \times (6 \times 8))} \\
 & := \frac{(9 \times (1 \times (5 - 3)))}{(2 \times (0 + ((7 - 4) \times 68)))} & := \frac{(9 \times (1 + (5 \times 3)))}{((20 + (7 \times 4)) \times 68)} & := \frac{(9 \times (1 + (5 - 3)))}{((20 \times (7 + (4 \times 6))) - 8)} \\
 & := \frac{(9 \times (15 - 3))}{((2 - (0 - 7)) \times (4 \times 68))} & := \frac{(9 \times (1^{53}))}{((20 \times 7) - (4 - 68))} & := \frac{(9 + (1 \times (5 \times 3)))}{((2^{07-4}) \times 68)} \\
 & := \frac{(9 + (1 + (5 - 3)))}{(2 \times (0 + ((7 + (4 + 6)) \times 8)))} & := \frac{(9 + (15 \times 3))}{(((2 \times (0 + 7)) + 4) \times 68)} & := \frac{(91 + (5 - 3))}{((20 + (7 + 4)) \times 68)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{9672}{135408}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{((9 - (6 - 7))^2)}{((135 + 40) \times 8)} & := \frac{((9 \times 6) - (7 \times 2))}{((1 - 3) \times ((5 - 40) \times 8))} & := \frac{((9 \times 6) - (7^2))}{(1 - (3 - ((5 + (4 - 0)) \times 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{((9 \times 6) - (7 + 2))}{(13 + ((5^4 + 0) - 8))} & := \frac{((9 + (6 + 7)) \times 2)}{(((1 + 3)^5) - 408)} & := \frac{((9 + (6 - 7)) \times 2)}{((1 + (3 \times (5 + (4 - 0)))) \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{((9 + 67) \times 2)}{((1 + 3) \times (540 - 8))} & := \frac{(9 - ((6 - 7) \times 2))}{(1 \times ((3 \times (54 - 0)) - 8))} & := \frac{(9 - (6 - (7 \times 2)))}{(1 - (3 - (5 \times (40 + 8))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(9 - (6 - (7^2)))}{(((13 + 5) \times 40) + 8)} & := \frac{(9 - (6 - (7 + 2)))}{(((1^3) + (5 \times (4 - 0))) \times 8)} & := \frac{(9 - (6 - (7 - 2)))}{(1 + (3 \times (5 - (4 \times (0 - 8)))))) \\
 & := \frac{(9 + ((6 + 7)^2))}{(((1 + 3) \times (5^4 + 0)) - 8)} & := \frac{(9 + ((6 - 7) \times 2))}{(1 - ((3 \times (5 - 40)) + 8))} & := \frac{(9 + (6 - (7 \times 2)))}{(1 - (35 - (40 + 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{(9 + (6 - (7 + 2)))}{(1 \times (3 \times ((5 \times (4 - 0)) + 8)))} & := \frac{(9 + (6 - (7 - 2)))}{(1 \times (35 \times (4 - (0 \times 8))))} & := \frac{(9 + (6 \times (7 - 2)))}{(1 - (3 - (540 + 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{(9 + (6 + (7 \times 2)))}{(1 \times (3 - (5 - 408)))} & := \frac{(9 + (6 + (7 + 2)))}{(1 + ((3 \times 5) + (40 \times 8)))} & := \frac{(9 + (67 - 2))}{(((1 + 3)^5) + (4 - (0 - 8)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.21 22 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15768}{39420} & := \frac{(((1^5) + (7 \times 6)) \times 8)}{((39 + 4) \times 20)} & := \frac{((1 - (5 + 7)) \times (6 - 8))}{(39 - (4 - 20))} & := \frac{(((1^{576}) \times 8)}{(3 + (9 + (4 \times (2 - 0))))} \\
 & := \frac{((1^5) \times (7 \times (6 + 8)))}{((3^{9-4}) + (2 - 0))} & := \frac{(((1 + (5 + (7 \times 6))) \times 8)}{((3 + 9) \times (4 \times 20))} & := \frac{(((1 + 5) \times (7 \times (6 \times 8)))}{((3 + 9) \times 420)} \\
 & := \frac{((1 - 5) \times (7 - (6 + 8)))}{((39 - 4) \times (2 - 0))} & := \frac{((15 + (7 - 6)) \times 8)}{((3 + (9 + 4)) \times 20)} & := \frac{((1 - 57) \times (6 - 8))}{((3 \times 94) - (2 - 0))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (5 - ((7 \times 6) - 8)))}{(3 \times (9 - (4 - 20)))} & := \frac{(1 - (5 - (76 - 8)))}{((3 + (9 - 4)) \times 20)} & := \frac{(1 \times (5 - ((7 - 6)^8)))}{(3 - (9 + (4 - 20)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (5 - (7 - (6 + 8))))}{(3 \times ((9 - 4) \times (2 - 0)))} & := \frac{(1 \times (5 \times (7 \times (6 + 8))))}{((39 - 4)^2 + 0)} & := \frac{(1 \times (5 + (7 - (6 - 8))))}{((3 \times (9 - 4)) + 20)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (5 + (7 + (6 - 8))))}{((3 \times 9) - (4 - (2 - 0)))} & := \frac{(1 + ((5 \times 7) - (6 - 8)))}{(3 + (94 - (2 - 0)))} & := \frac{(1 + (5 - (7 \times (6 - 8))))}{(((3 + 9) \times 4) + (2 - 0))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (5^{(7-6)^8}))}{(39 - (4 + 20))} & := \frac{(1 + (5 + (76 + 8)))}{((3 \times (9 - 4))^2 + 0)} & := \frac{(1 + (57 - (6 + 8)))}{((3 \times (9 \times 4)) + (2 - 0))} \\
 & := \frac{(15 \times ((7 - 6) \times 8))}{(3 \times ((9 - 4) \times 20))} & & &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18370}{64295} & := \frac{(((1^8) + 3)^7 + 0)}{((64^2) \times (9 + 5))} & := \frac{(((1 + 8) \times 3) - (7 - 0))}{(6 + (4 \times (2^{9-5})))} & := \frac{(((1 + 8) \times 3) + (7 - 0))}{(64 + ((2 + 9) \times 5))} \\
 & := \frac{(((1^{83}) + (7 - 0))}{(6 + ((4 \times 2) + (9 + 5)))} & := \frac{(((1^8) - (3 - 70))}{((6 \times 42) - (9 + 5))} & := \frac{(((1^8) \times (3 + (7 - 0)))}{(6 - ((4^2) - (9 \times 5)))} \\
 & := \frac{(((1^8) + (3 + 70))}{((6 \times (4 \times (2 + 9))) - 5)} & := \frac{(((1 + (8 + 3)) \times (7 - 0))}{(6 \times ((4 \times (2 + 9)) + 5))} & := \frac{(((1 + (8 - 3)) \times (7 - 0))}{(6 - (4 - (29 \times 5)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (8 - (3 \times (7 - 0))))}{(6 - (4 - (2 + (9 \times 5))))} & := \frac{(1 - (8 + (3 - 70)))}{(6 \times ((4^2) - 9) \times 5)} & := \frac{(1 \times ((8 \times 3) + 70))}{(((6^4-2) \times 9) + 5)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (3 + (7 - 0))))}{((6 + 4) \times (2 \times (9 + 5)))} & := \frac{(1 \times (8 + (3 - (7 - 0))))}{(6 - (4 \times (2 - (9 - 5))))} & := \frac{(1 \times (8 + (3 + (7 - 0))))}{(((6 - 4) \times 29) + 5)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + ((8 \times 3) + (7 - 0)))}{((6 + (4 - 2)) \times (9 + 5))} & := \frac{(1 + (8 - (3 - 70)))}{((6 \times 42) + (9 + 5))} & := \frac{(1 + (8 + (3 \times (7 - 0))))}{((6 + (4 + (2 + 9))) \times 5)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (8 + (37 - 0)))}{(64 + (2 + 95))} & := \frac{(18 - (3 - (7 - 0)))}{(((6 + (4 - 2)) \times 9) + 5)} & := \frac{(18 \times (3 + (7 - 0)))}{((6 + (4 \times 2)) \times (9 \times 5))} \\
 & := \frac{(18 + (3 + (7 - 0)))}{(6 + (4 \times ((2 \times 9) + 5)))} & & &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18534}{92670} &:= \frac{((1 + (8 + 5)) \times (3 \times 4))}{(((9 \times 2) - 6) \times 70)} := \frac{((1 + 8) \times 534)}{(9 \times 2670)} := \frac{(1 - ((8 - (5 \times 3)) \times 4))}{((9^2) - (6 - 70))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (8 - ((5 - 3)^4)))}{(9 \times ((2 \times 6) - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 - (8 \times (5 - (3 + 4))))}{((9 \times 2) + (67 - 0))} := \frac{(1 \times (((8 - 5)^3) - 4))}{((9 \times (2 \times 6)) + (7 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 - (5 - (3 + 4))))}{(92 - (6 \times (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 - (5 - (3 - 4))))}{(9 + (2 + (6 - (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 - (5 + (3 - 4))))}{(9 - (2 - (6 + (7 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 + ((5 \times 3) + 4)))}{(9 \times (2 + (6 + (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 + (5 - (3 - 4))))}{((9 - (2 + 6)) \times 70)} := \frac{(1 \times (8 + (5 + (3 - 4))))}{((9 \times 2) + (6 \times (7 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{1^{8534}}{((9^2) - (6 + 70))} := \frac{(1 + (((8 - 5)^3) \times 4))}{((92 \times 6) - (7 - 0))} := \frac{(1 + (8 - (5 - (3 \times 4))))}{(9 + ((2^6) + (7 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (8 - (5 - (3 - 4))))}{(9 - ((2^6) - 70))} := \frac{(1 + (8 - (5 + (3 - 4))))}{(92 - (67 - 0))} := \frac{(1 + (8 \times (5 - (3 - 4))))}{((9 + 26) \times (7 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (8 + (5 - (3 + 4))))}{(9 + (2 \times (6 + (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 + (8 + (5 - (3 - 4))))}{(9 + (2 - (6 - 70)))} := \frac{(1 + (8 + (5 + (3 + 4))))}{(9 + (26 + 70))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (8 + (5 + (3 - 4))))}{(9 + ((2 + 6) \times (7 - 0)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{25496}{31870} &:= \frac{(((2^5) - 4) \times (9 \times 6))}{(3 \times ((1 + 8) \times 70))} := \frac{((2 - (5 - (4 + 9))) \times 6)}{(3 \times (18 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{((2 \times 54) + 96)}{((31 \times 8) + (7 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^5) - (4 \times (9 - 6)))}{(((3 + 1) \times 8) - (7 - 0))} := \frac{((2^5) \times ((4 \times 9) + 6))}{(3 \times (1 \times (8 \times 70)))} := \frac{((2^5) \times (4 + (9 - 6)))}{((3 + (1^8)) \times 70)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + (5 - (4 - 9))) \times 6)}{(3 + (1 \times (87 - 0)))} := \frac{((2 + 54) \times (9 \times 6))}{(3 \times (18 \times 70))} := \frac{((2 + 54) \times (9 - 6))}{(3 \times ((1^8) \times 70))} \\
 &:= \frac{((25 + 4) \times 96)}{((3 + 1) \times 870)} := \frac{(2 - ((5 \times 4) - (9 \times 6)))}{(3 \times (1 \times (8 + (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(2 - (5 - (4 + (9 - 6))))}{(3 + (1 + (8 - (7 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (5 - (49 + 6)))}{(3 - (1 \times (8 - 70)))} := \frac{(2 - (5 \times ((4 - 9) \times 6)))}{(3 + (187 - 0))} := \frac{(2 - (54 - 96))}{(3 - (18 - 70))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 9)) + 6))}{(31 \times (8 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(2 \times (5 - (4 - (9 - 6))))}{(3 + ((1^8) \times (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(2 \times (5 + (4 + (9 + 6))))}{(3 + (1 + (8 \times (7 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (5 + (4 + (9 - 6))))}{(31 - (8 - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(2^{5-4+9-6})}{((3 \times (1 + 8)) - (7 - 0))} := \frac{(2^{5+4-9+6})}{(3 - (1 - (8 + 70)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + ((5 - 4) \times (9 \times 6)))}{((3 - (1 - 8)) \times (7 - 0))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{26910}{75348} &:= \frac{(((2 \times 6) + 9) \times 10)}{((7^5-3) \times (4 + 8))} := \frac{(((2^6) - 9) \times 10)}{(7 \times ((53 \times 4) + 8))} := \frac{((2 \times (6 + 9)) + 10)}{((7 - (5 - (3 \times 4))) \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (6 + 9)) - 10)}{(7 + (53 + (4 - 8)))} := \frac{((2^6) - (9 - 10))}{(7 + (5 \times (3 + (4 \times 8))))} := \frac{((2^6) \times (9 + (1 - 0)))}{(7 \times ((5 + 3) \times (4 \times 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + (6 \times 9)) \times 10)}{((7^5-3) \times (4 \times 8))} := \frac{((2 + (6 + 9)) \times 10)}{(7 \times ((5 \times (3 \times 4)) + 8))} := \frac{((2 + 6) \times (9 + (1 - 0)))}{(7 \times ((5 + (3 - 4)) \times 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{((26 \times 9) + (1 - 0))}{(7 \times (5 + ((3^4) + 8)))} := \frac{((26 + 9) \times 10)}{(((7 + 5) \times (3^4)) + 8)} := \frac{(2 - (6 - (9 \times (1 - 0))))}{(7 - (5 + (3 \times (4 - 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (6 - (9 + 10)))}{(7 + (5 \times (3 - (4 - 8))))} := \frac{(2 \times (6 \times (9 + (1 - 0))))}{(7 \times ((5 - (3 - 4)) \times 8))} := \frac{(2 \times (6 + (9 \times (1 - 0))))}{(7 \times (5 + (3 - (4 - 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (6 + (9 + 10)))}{(7 \times (5 + (3 + (4 + 8))))} := \frac{(2 \times (6 + (9 - 10)))}{(7 \times (5 + (3 + (4 - 8))))} := \frac{(2 \times (69 + (1 - 0)))}{(7 \times (5 + (3 + 48)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + ((6 \times 9) - (1 - 0)))}{(((7 - 5) \times (3^4)) - 8)} := \frac{(26 + (9 \times (1 - 0)))}{(7 \times (5 - (3 - (4 + 8))))} := \frac{(26 + (9 + 10))}{(75 + (3 + 48))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(26 + (9 - 10))}{(7 + ((5 \times 3) + 48))}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{30852}{69417} &:= \frac{(((3 \times (0 + 8))^5) \times 2)}{((6 + (9 - (4 - 1)))^7)} := \frac{(((30 + 8) \times 5) + 2)}{(6 + (9 + 417))} := \frac{(((30 - 8) \times 5) + 2)}{(6 \times ((9 - (4 - 1)) \times 7))} \\ &:= \frac{((3 - ((0 \times 8) - 5)) \times 2)}{(6 + (9 + (4 + 17)))} := \frac{((3 - (0 - (8 + 5))) \times 2)}{(6 \times (9 + (4 - (1^7))))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 \times 8)) + 52)}{(6 + (94 + 17))} \\ &:= \frac{((3 \times (0 - 8)) + 52)}{(6 + (9 + (41 + 7)))} := \frac{((30 \times (8 - 5)) + 2)}{(69 \times (4 - (1^7)))} := \frac{((30 \times (8 - 5)) - 2)}{(6 \times (9 - (4 \times (1 - 7))))} \\ &:= \frac{((30 \times 8) + 52)}{(6 + ((94 - 1) \times 7))} := \frac{((30 + (8 \times 5)) \times 2)}{((6 + 9) \times (4 + 17))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - ((8 - 5)^2)))}{(6 + (9 + (4 + (1 + 7))))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 - (0 - (8 - (5 + 2))))}{(6 - (9 - (4 + (1 + 7))))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (8 - (5 - 2))))}{(6 - (9 - (4 + 17)))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (8 + (5^2))))}{(69 + (4 + (1 + 7)))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (8 \times (5 \times 2))))}{(6 \times (9 \times (4 - (1 - 7))))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (8 \times (5 - 2))))}{(6 \times (9 \times (4 - (1^7))))} := \frac{(3 + (0 - (8 - (5^2))))}{(6 - (9 - (41 + 7)))} \\ &:= \frac{(30 - ((8 - 5) \times 2))}{(((6 + 9) \times 4) + (1 - 7))} := \frac{(30 + ((8 + 5) \times 2))}{(6 \times (9 + (4 + (1 + 7))))} := \frac{(30 + (8 + (5 \times 2)))}{(6 + (94 + (1 + 7)))} \\ &:= \frac{(308 \times (5 + 2))}{((694 - 1) \times 7)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{39012}{48765} &:= \frac{(((3 \times (9 - 0)) + 1) \times 2)}{(4 + (8 - (7 - 65)))} := \frac{(((3 \times (9 - 0)) - 1) \times 2)}{((4 + (8 + (7 - 6))) \times 5)} := \frac{(((3 - 9) \times (0 - 1)) + 2)}{(4 + (((8 - 7)^6) + 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(((3 - 9) \times (0 - 1)) - 2)}{(4 + (8 - (7 \times (6 - 5))))} := \frac{((3 - (9 \times (0 - 1)))^2)}{(4 \times (8 + (7 + (6 \times 5))))} := \frac{((3 \times (9 - (0 - 1))) + 2)}{(48 - (7 + (6 - 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{((3 \times (9 - (0 - 1))) - 2)}{(4 + (8 - (7 - (6 \times 5))))} := \frac{((3 \times (90 \times 1)) + 2)}{(4 \times (8 + (7 \times (6 + 5))))} := \frac{((3 \times (90 \times 1)) - 2)}{(4 + ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5))} \\ &:= \frac{((3 + (90 + 1)) \times 2)}{((4 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6 + 5))} := \frac{((3 - 9) \times (0 - 12))}{(4 + (87 - (6 - 5)))} := \frac{((39 + (0 - 1)) \times 2)}{(48 + ((7 \times 6) + 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times ((9 + (0 - 1)) \times 2))}{(4 \times (8 + (7 \times (6 - 5))))} := \frac{(3 \times ((9 + (0 - 1))^2))}{(48 \times ((7 - 6) \times 5))} := \frac{(3 \times (9 - (0 - (1 + 2))))}{((4 - (8 - (7 + 6))) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (90 - (1 \times 2)))}{(3 \times (90 + (1 \times 2)))} := \frac{(3 \times (90 + (1 \times 2)))}{(3 \times (90 + (1 \times 2)))} := \frac{(3 + (9 - (0 \times 12)))}{(3 + (9 - (0 \times 12)))} \\ &:= \frac{((4 \times (8 + 7)) + 6) \times 5}{((4 \times (8 + 7)) + 6) \times 5} := \frac{(4 + ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5))}{(4 + ((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5)))} := \frac{(39 - (0 - (1^2)))}{(4 + ((8 - 7) \times 6)) \times 5} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (9 - (0 - 12)))}{(4 + (8 + (7 + (6 + 5))))} := \frac{(3 + (90 + (1 + 2)))}{(4 \times ((8 - 7) \times (6 \times 5)))} := \frac{(39 - (0 - (1^2)))}{((4 + ((8 - 7) \times 6)) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(390 - (1 \times 2))}{((4 + (87 + 6)) \times 5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{41067}{95823} &:= \frac{((4 - (1 + (0 - 6))) \times 7)}{(((9 - (5 - 8))^2) + 3)} := \frac{((4 - (1 - 0)) \times (6 \times 7))}{((9 + (5 \times 8)) \times (2 \times 3))} := \frac{((4 \times (1 - (0 - 6))) - 7)}{(9 - (5 \times (8 \times (2 - 3))))} \\ &:= \frac{((4 \times (10 - 6)) - 7)}{(9 + (5 + (8 + (2 - 3))))} := \frac{((4 + 10) \times (6 \times 7))}{(((9 \times 5) - 8)^2) + 3} := \frac{(4 - (1 - (0 \times 67)))}{(9 + (5 - (8 + (2 - 3))))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - (1 + (0 - (6 \times 7))))}{((9 + ((5 + 8) \times 2)) \times 3)} := \frac{(4 \times (1 \times (0 + (6 \times 7))))}{((9 + (5 \times 8)) \times (2^3))} := \frac{(4 \times (10 + (6 - 7)))}{(4 \times (10 + (6 - 7)))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + ((1^{06}) + 7))}{(9 + (5 + (8 + (2 \times 3))))} := \frac{(4 + (1 - (0 - (6 + 7))))}{(9 + ((5 + (8 - 2)) \times 3))} := \frac{(4 + (1 + (0 - (6 - 7))))}{(9 + (5 - (8 - (2^3))))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (10 - (6 - 7)))}{(9 - (5 - (8 + 23)))} := \frac{(4 + (10 + (6 + 7)))}{(9 \times (5 + (8 - (2 \times 3))))} := \frac{(4 + (10 + 67))}{(9 \times (5 + (8 + (2^3))))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(4 + (106 + 7))}{((9 \times (5 \times (8 - 2))) + 3)} := \frac{(41 - ((0 \times 6) - 7))}{((9 \times (5 + 8)) - (2 + 3))} := \frac{(41 - (0 - (6 + 7)))}{(9 \times (5 + (8 - (2 - 3))))} \\ &:= \frac{(41 - (0 - 67))}{((9 + 5) \times ((8 - 2) \times 3))} := \frac{(41 + (0 - (6 - 7)))}{(95 + (8 - (2 + 3)))} := \frac{(410 - (6 - 7))}{(958 - (2 - 3))} \\ &:= \frac{(410 + (6 + 7))}{((9 + (5 \times (8^2))) \times 3)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{46312}{57890} &:= \frac{(4 \times ((6^3 - 1) \times 2))}{((5 + (7 - 8)) \times 90)} := \frac{(4 \times ((6^3 - 1) + 2))}{((5 \times (7 \times 8)) - 90)} := \frac{(4 \times ((6 + 3) \times 12))}{((5 - (7 - 8)) \times 90)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times ((6 + 31) \times 2))}{((5 \times (7 \times 8)) + 90)} := \frac{(4 \times (6 - (3 - (1 + 2))))}{(5 \times (7 + (8 - (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 \times (6 - (3 \times (1^2))))}{(5 - (7 - (8 + (9 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 \times ((3 + 1)^2))}{(5 \times (7 + (89 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times (6 \times (3 + (1^2))))}{(5 \times (7 + (8 + (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 \times (6^3 - 1^2))}{((5 + (7 + 8)) \times (9 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 + ((3 + 1)^2))}{(5 + (7 + (8 + 90)))} := \frac{(4 \times (6 + (3 - (1^2))))}{(5 \times (7 - (8 - (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 \times (6 + (3 \times (1 + 2))))}{((5 \times (7 + 8)) + 90)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 + (3 + 12)))}{(((5 + 7) \times 8) + (9 - 0))} := \frac{(4 \times (63 - (1 + 2)))}{((5 \times 78) - 90)} := \frac{(4 \times (63 + (1 \times 2)))}{(5 \times ((7 \times 8) + (9 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(4^{6-3 \times 1^2})}{(5 - (7 + (8 - 90)))} := \frac{(4 + ((6 \times 31) - 2))}{(5 \times ((7 \times 8) - (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 + ((6^3 - 1) \times 2))}{(5 - ((7 - 8) \times 90))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + ((6 + (3 - 1)^2))}{((5 \times (7 - 8)) + 90)} := \frac{(4 + ((6 + 3) \times 12))}{(5 + ((7 + 8) \times (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 + 6312)}{(5 + 7890)} \\ &:= \frac{(46 \times (3 + (1 + 2)))}{(5 \times (78 - (9 - 0)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{76320}{91584} &:= \frac{((7 - (6 - 3)) \times 20)}{((9 + 15) \times (8 - 4))} := \frac{((7 \times (6 + 3)) + (2 - 0))}{(9 - (15 - 84))} := \frac{((7 + (6 \times 3)) \times 20)}{((9 + 1) \times (5 \times (8 + 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{((7 + (6 + 3)) \times 20)}{((91 + 5) \times (8 - 4))} := \frac{((7 + (6 - 3)) \times (2 - 0))}{((9 + (1 \times (5 - 8))) \times 4)} := \frac{((7 + (6 - 3)) \times 20)}{(9 - (1 - (58 \times 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{((7 + (6 - 3))^2 + 0)}{((9 + (1^5)) \times (8 + 4))} := \frac{((7 + 63) \times (2 - 0))}{(9 - (1 - (5 \times (8 \times 4))))} := \frac{((7 - 6) \times (3 \times 20))}{(9 \times (1 - (5 - (8 + 4))))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 - (6 - (3^2 + 0)))}{(9 + (15 - (8 + 4)))} := \frac{(7 \times ((6 - 3) \times 20))}{(9 \times ((1 + (5 + 8)) \times 4))} := \frac{(7 \times (6 - (3 - (2 - 0))))}{(9 + ((1^5) + (8 \times 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 \times (6 \times (3 + (2 - 0))))}{(9 \times (1 - (5 - (8 \times 4))))} := \frac{(7 \times (6 + (3^2 + 0)))}{(((9 + 1) \times (5 + 8)) - 4)} := \frac{(7 + ((6 \times 3) - 20))}{(9 - (15 - (8 + 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + ((6 + 3) \times (2 - 0)))}{(9 + (1 + (5 \times (8 - 4))))} := \frac{(7 + (6 - (3 - 20)))}{(9 - (1 \times (5 - (8 \times 4))))} := \frac{(7 + (6 + (32 - 0)))}{(9 + (1 + ((5 \times 8) + 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + (63 + 20))}{(9 + (15 + 84))} := \frac{(7 + (63 - 20))}{(9 - (1 - ((5 + 8) \times 4)))} := \frac{(76 - (3 - (2 - 0)))}{(9 \times (1 + (5 + (8 - 4))))} \\ &:= \frac{(76 - (3 \times (2 - 0)))}{((9 - (1 - (5 + 8))) \times 4)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1935}{278640} &:= \frac{(((1^9) + 3) \times 5)}{(((2^7) - 8) \times (6 \times (4 - 0)))} := \frac{((1^{93}) \times 5)}{(2 \times ((7 + (8 - 6)) \times 40))} := \frac{((1^{93}) + 5)}{(27 \times (8 + (6 \times (4 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{((1^9) - (3 - 5))}{(27 \times (8 \times (6 - (4 - 0))))} := \frac{((1^9) \times (3 \times 5))}{(27 \times (8 \times (6 + (4 - 0))))} := \frac{((1^9) + (3 \times 5))}{((2^7) \times (8 + (6 + (4 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{((1^9) + (3 + 5))}{((2 + (7 - 8)) \times (6^4 + 0))} := \frac{((1^9) + 35)}{(27 \times (8 \times (6 \times (4 - 0))))} := \frac{((1 + (9 - 3)) \times 5)}{(((2^7) - (8 - 6)) \times 40)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(19-3) \times 5}{((2^7) \times (86 + (4-0)))} &:= \frac{(1 - (9 - 35))}{((2 - (7 - 8)) \times (6^4 + 0))} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((9 \times 3) + 5))}{((2 + 7) \times (8 \times (64 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (9 \times 35))}{((27 + 8) \times (6^4 + 0))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (9 + (3 - 5)))}{(2 \times (7 \times (8 + (64 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(1^{935})}{(2 + (78 + (64 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + ((9 \times 3) - 5))}{((2 + 7) \times (8 \times (6 + 40)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (9 - (3 + 5)))}{(278 + (6 + (4 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (9 - (3 - 5)))}{(27 \times (8^{6-4+0}))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (9 + 35))}{(((2 \times 78) + 6) \times 40)} &:= \frac{(19 - (3 \times 5))}{(2 + (7 \times (86 - (4 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(19 + 35)}{((2 + 7) \times (864 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(193 + 5)}{(((2 \times 7) + 8) \times (6^4 + 0))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{6054}{193728}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((6 - (0 - 5)) \times 4)}{((19 + 3) \times (72 - 8))} &:= \frac{((6 \times (0 + 5)) + 4)}{((1 + (9 \times (3 \times (7 - 2)))) \times 8)} &:= \frac{((6 + (0 - 5)) \times 4)}{(1 + ((9 \times (3 \times (7 - 2))) - 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 + (0 - 5))^4)}{(1 \times (9 + ((3 \times (7 - 2)) + 8)))} &:= \frac{((60 \times 5) + 4)}{(((1^9) + 37) \times (2^8))} &:= \frac{((60 \times 5) - 4)}{((1 - (9 \times (3 - 7))) \times (2^8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 - ((0 \times 5) - 4))}{((1 + (9 + (3 + 7))) \times (2 \times 8))} &:= \frac{(6 - (0 - (5 \times 4)))}{((1 + (9 + 3)) \times (72 - 8))} &:= \frac{(6 - (0 - (5 + 4)))}{(1 \times ((9 + (3 \times 7)) \times (2 \times 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 - (0 - (5 - 4)))}{((1 + (9 - (3 - 7))) \times (2 \times 8))} &:= \frac{(6 - (0 \times 54))}{(1 \times ((9 + (3 \times (7 - 2))) \times 8))} &:= \frac{(6 - (0 - 54))}{((1 + 9) \times (3 \times (72 - 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times ((0 \times 5) + 4))}{(1 \times ((9 + 3) \times (72 - 8)))} &:= \frac{(6 \times (0 + (5 \times 4)))}{((19 + (3 - 7)) \times (2^8))} &:= \frac{(6 \times (0 + (5 + 4)))}{(1 \times (9 \times (3 \times (72 - 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 + ((0 \times 5) - 4))}{(1 + (9 - (3 - ((7^2) + 8))))} &:= \frac{(6 + (0 - (5 - 4)))}{(1 \times ((9 - (3 - (7 \times 2))) \times 8))} &:= \frac{(60 - (5 \times 4))}{(1 \times ((9 + (3 - 7)) \times (2^8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(60 \times (5 + 4))}{((1 + 9) \times (3 \times (72 \times 8)))} &:= \frac{(60 + (5 \times 4))}{((1^9) \times ((3 + 7) \times (2^8)))} &:= \frac{(60 + (5 - 4))}{(1 \times ((9 \times (3 \times 72)) + 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(60 + 54)}{(19 \times (3 \times (72 - 8)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{8046}{132759}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((8 - (0 - 4)) \times 6)}{((13 - 2) \times ((7 + 5) \times 9))} &:= \frac{((8 \times (0 + 4)) - 6)}{(1 \times ((3 \times (2^7)) + (5 \times 9)))} &:= \frac{((8 + (0 - 4)) \times 6)}{(1 \times (3 \times (2 \times (7 + 59))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((8 + (0 - 4))^6)}{(132 \times ((7 - 5)^9))} &:= \frac{(8 - ((0 \times 4) - 6))}{((13 - 2) \times (7 + (5 + 9)))} &:= \frac{(8 - (0 - (4 \times 6)))}{((1 + 3) \times (2 \times (7 + 59)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 - (0 - (4 + 6)))}{((1 + ((3 \times (2 + 7)) + 5)) \times 9)} &:= \frac{(8 - (0 - (4 - 6)))}{(1 \times (3 - (2 - (7 \times (5 + 9)))))} &:= \frac{(8 - (0 \times 46))}{((1 + (3 - 2)) \times (7 + 59))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 - (0 - 46))}{(132 + 759)} &:= \frac{(8 \times ((0 \times 4) + 6))}{(1 + (32 + 759))} &:= \frac{(8 \times (0 - (4 - 6)))}{(1 \times (3 \times (2 \times ((7 \times 5) + 9))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 \times (0 + 46))}{((1 + 3) \times (2 \times 759))} &:= \frac{(8^{0-4+6})}{(((1 + 3)^2) \times (7 + 59))} &:= \frac{(8 + ((0 \times 4) - 6))}{(1 \times (3 + (2 - (7 \times (5 - 9)))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 + (0 - (4 - 6)))}{(1 \times ((32 \times 7) - 59))} &:= \frac{(80 - (4 \times 6))}{((13 - 2) \times (75 + 9))} &:= \frac{(80 - (4 - 6))}{(1 \times (3 + (2 \times (75 \times 9))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(80 + (4 \times 6))}{((1 + 32) \times (7 + (5 \times 9)))} &:= \frac{(80 + (4 + 6))}{(((13 \times 2) + 7) \times (5 \times 9))} &:= \frac{(80 + 46)}{(1 \times (3 \times ((2 + 75) \times 9)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(80 - 46)}{(1 \times (3 \times ((2^7) + 59)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{9531}{247806}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((9 + 5) \times 3) + 1)}{((2 + (4 + 7)) \times (80 + 6))} &:= \frac{(((9 - 5) \times 3) + 1)}{(2 + (4 \times (78 - (0 - 6))))} &:= \frac{((9 \times (5 + 3)) - 1)}{(((2^4) + 7) \times 80) + 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(9 \times 5) + (3 \times 1)}{((2 - (4 \times 7)) \times (8 \times (0 - 6)))} := \frac{((9 \times 5) + 31)}{(247 \times (8 - (0 \times 6)))} := \frac{((9 + 5) \times (3 \times 1))}{(2 \times ((4 + (7 + 80)) \times 6))} \\
 & := \frac{(9 - (5 - (3 \times 1)))}{((2 \times ((4 + 7) \times (8 - 0))) + 6)} := \frac{(9 - (5 - (3 - 1)))}{((2 - ((4 - 7) \times (8 - 0))) \times 6)} := \frac{(9 - (5 + (3 \times 1)))}{(2 \times (4 + (7 + (8 + (0 - 6)))))} \\
 & := \frac{(9 \times (5 - (3 - 1)))}{(2 \times ((4 \times 7) - (8 + (0 - 6))))} := \frac{(9 \times ((5 \times 3) + 1))}{(2 \times (4 \times (78 \times (0 + 6))))} := \frac{(9 \times (5 - (3 \times 1)))}{(2 \times ((47 - (8 - 0)) \times 6))} \\
 & := \frac{(9 \times (5 - (3 - 1)))}{((2 \times (4 \times (7 + 80))) + 6)} := \frac{(9 \times (5 + (3 \times 1)))}{(24 \times (78 - (0 \times 6)))} := \frac{(9^{5-3-1})}{(((2 + (4 \times 7)) \times (8 - 0)) - 6)} \\
 & := \frac{(9 + ((5 \times 3) + 1))}{(2 + (((4 \times 7) + 80) \times 6))} := \frac{(9 + ((5^3) - 1))}{(247 \times (8 - (0 - 6)))} := \frac{(9 + (5 - (3 + 1)))}{((2 \times (47 + 80)) + 6)} \\
 & := \frac{(9 + (5 \times (3 \times 1)))}{(2 \times (4 \times (78 - (0 \times 6))))} := \frac{(9 + (5 \times (3 - 1)))}{(2 + ((4 + (78 - 0)) \times 6))} := \frac{(9 + (5^{3-1}))}{(2 \times (4 - ((7 - 80) \times 6)))} \\
 & := \frac{(9 + (5 + (3 \times 1)))}{((2 \times (4 \times (7 \times (8 - 0)))) - 6)}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.22 23 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10452}{67938} & := \frac{(((1^{04}) + 5)^2)}{(6 \times ((7 \times 9) - (3 \times 8)))} := \frac{((1 - (0 - 45)) \times 2)}{((67 \times 9) + (3 - 8))} := \frac{((1^{04}) \times (5 \times 2))}{(67 + (9 - (3 + 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{((10 \times (4 \times 5)) + 2)}{((6 + 7) \times (93 + 8))} := \frac{((10 \times (4 \times 5)) - 2)}{((6 + 7) \times (9 \times (3 + 8)))} := \frac{((10 + (4 \times 5)) \times 2)}{(6 + ((7 + 9) \times (3 \times 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (0 - (4 - (5 - 2))))}{(6 - (7 - (9 - (3 - 8))))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (4 + (5 - 2))))}{(67 + (9 - (3 \times 8)))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 - (4 - 52)))}{(6 \times (7 - (9 \times (3 - 8))))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (4 \times (5 \times 2))))}{((6 \times (7 \times (9 - 3))) + 8)} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (4 \times (5 + 2))))}{(6 + ((7 + 9) \times (3 + 8)))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (4^{5-2})))}{((6 \times (7 \times 9)) + 38)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (4 + (5 \times 2))))}{((6 \times (7 + 9)) + (3 - 8))} := \frac{(1 + (0 - (4 - (5^2))))}{((6 \times 7) + (93 + 8))} := \frac{(1 + (0 - (4 - (5 + 2))))}{((6 \times (7 - 9)) + 38)} \\
 & := \frac{(10 - (4 - (5 \times 2)))}{(6 + (7 \times (9 - (3 - 8))))} := \frac{(10 \times ((4 \times 5) + 2))}{((6 \times (79 \times 3)) + 8)} := \frac{(10 \times (4 + (5 - 2)))}{((6 + 7) \times ((9 \times 3) + 8))} \\
 & := \frac{(10 + ((4 \times 5) + 2))}{((6 - (7 - (9 \times 3))) \times 8)} := \frac{(10 + (4 \times (5 + 2)))}{(((6 + 79) \times 3) - 8)} := \frac{(10 + (4 + (5 \times 2)))}{(6 \times (7 + ((9 \times 3) - 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{(10 + (4 + 52))}{((6 + 7) \times (9 + (3 \times 8)))} := \frac{(104 - (5 \times 2))}{((6 + 7) \times (9 + 38))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17064}{93852} & := \frac{(((1 + (7 - 0)) \times 6) - 4)}{(((9 - 3) \times (8 \times 5)) + 2)} := \frac{(((1^7) + 0) \times (6 \times 4))}{((9 + 3) \times (8 + (5 - 2)))} := \frac{(((1^7) + 0) \times 64)}{((9 \times 38) + (5 \times 2))} \\
 & := \frac{((1 + (7 + (0 - 6)))^4)}{(93 - (8 - (5 - 2)))} := \frac{((17 \times (0 + 6)) - 4)}{((9 \times 3) + (8^{5-2}))} := \frac{(1 - (7 + (0 - (6 + 4))))}{(9 + (38 - (5^2)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times ((7 \times (0 + 6)) - 4))}{((9 \times (3 \times 8)) - (5 + 2))} := \frac{(1 \times (7 \times ((0 \times 6) + 4)))}{(((9 + 3) \times (8 + 5)) - 2)} := \frac{(1 \times (7 \times (0 + (6 + 4))))}{((9 \times (3 + (8 \times 5))) - 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (70 - (6 + 4)))}{((9 + (3 \times 8)) \times (5 \times 2))} := \frac{(1 \times (70 + 64))}{((93 \times 8) - (5 + 2))} := \frac{(1 \times (706 - 4))}{(9 + 3852)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + ((7 + (0 - 6)))^4)}{(9 - (3 - (8 - (5 - 2))))} := \frac{(1 + (7 - ((0 \times 6) - 4)))}{(9 - (3 - (8 + 52)))} := \frac{(1 + (7 - (0 - (6 \times 4))))}{(9 - (3 - (85 \times 2)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (7 - (0 - (6 + 4))))}{(9 + (3 + (85 + 2)))} := \frac{(1 + (7 - (0 - (6 - 4))))}{(93 - ((8 \times 5) - 2))} := \frac{(1 + (7 - (0 \times 64)))}{(9 - (3 - ((8 \times 5) - 2)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(1 + (7 - (0 - 64)))}{(9 + (385 + 2))} &:= \frac{(1 + (7^{06-4}))}{(9 + (38 \times (5 + 2)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (7 + (0 - (6 - 4))))}{(93 - (8 + 52))} \\ &:= \frac{(17 \times (0 + (6 + 4)))}{(938 - (5 - 2))} &:= \frac{(170 + (6 + 4))}{(9 \times ((3 + 8) \times (5 \times 2)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{17496}{58320} &:= \frac{(((1 + (7 + 4)) \times 9) - 6)}{(5 \times (8 + (3 \times 20)))} &:= \frac{(1 + 7)^4 \times 96}{5 \times 8^{3 \times 2} + 0} &:= \frac{((1 - (7 - 49)) \times 6)}{(((5 \times 8) + 3) \times 20)} \\ &:= \frac{((1^{74}) \times (9 - 6))}{(5 \times (8 - (3 \times (2 - 0))))} &:= \frac{((1^{74}) \times 96)}{((5 + (8 + 3)) \times 20)} &:= \frac{((1 + (7 \times 4)) \times (9 - 6))}{(58 \times (3 + (2 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + (7 - 4)) \times 96)}{(5 \times (8 \times (32 - 0)))} &:= \frac{((17 - 4) \times (9 - 6))}{(5 \times ((8 \times 3) + (2 - 0)))} &:= \frac{((17 - 4) \times 96)}{(5 \times (832 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - ((7 \times (4 - 9)) + 6))}{((5 + (8 - 3))^2 + 0)} &:= \frac{(1 - ((7 \times (4 - 9)) - 6))}{((5 \times (8 \times 3)) + 20)} &:= \frac{(1 \times (((7 - 4) \times 9) + 6))}{(5 \times ((8 + 3) \times (2 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times ((7 + (4 - 9)) \times 6))}{(5 \times (8^{3-2+0}))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (7 - (4 - (9 - 6))))}{(5 - (8 - (3 + 20)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (74 \times (9 - 6)))}{(((5 \times 8) - 3) \times 20)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (7 + (4 - (9 - 6))))}{(5 + (8 - (3 - 20)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (7 + (4^{9-6})))}{(5 \times (8 \times (3 \times (2 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(1 + (7 + (4 + (9 \times 6))))}{(5 \times ((8 \times 3) + 20))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (7 + (4 + (9 + 6))))}{(5 + (83 + (2 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (7 + (4 + (9 - 6))))}{(5 \times ((8 - 3) \times (2 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (7 + (4 + 96)))}{(5 \times (8 \times (3^2 + 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (74 - (9 \times 6)))}{(5 \times (8 + (3 \times (2 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(1 + (74 - (9 + 6)))}{(5 \times (8 \times (3 + (2 - 0))))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{32184}{75096} &:= \frac{(3 - (2 - (1 \times (8 \times 4))))}{(7 \times (5 - ((0 \times 9) - 6)))} &:= \frac{(3 \times ((2 \times (1 \times 8)) + 4))}{(7 \times (5 - (0 - (9 + 6))))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (2 - (1 - (8 + 4))))}{(7 + ((5 - (0 - 9)) \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (2 - (1 - (8 - 4))))}{(7 \times (5 - (0 \times 96)))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (2 \times ((1 + 8) \times 4))}{((75 - (0 - 9)) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(3 \times (2 \times (1 \times (8 - 4))))}{(7 \times (5 - (0 - (9 - 6))))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (2 \times (1^{84})))}{(7 \times (5 + (0 - (9 - 6))))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (2 + (1 \times (8 + 4))))}{(7 - (5 + (0 - 96)))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (2 + (1 \times (8 - 4))))}{(7 \times ((5 \times (0 \times 9)) + 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (2 + (1 + (8 \times 4))))}{(7 \times (50 - (9 + 6)))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (2 + (1 + (8 + 4))))}{(7 \times (5 \times (0 + (9 - 6))))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (2 + (1 + (8 - 4))))}{(7^{5-09+6})} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (2 + (18 \times 4)))}{(((7 - (5 - 0))^9) + 6)} &:= \frac{(3 \times (21 \times (8 - 4)))}{(7 \times ((5 - (0 - 9)) \times 6))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (21 + (8 \times 4)))}{(7 \times (50 + (9 - 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (21 + 84))}{(750 - (9 + 6))} &:= \frac{(3^{2-1^{84}})}{(7 - (5 \times (0 \times 96)))} &:= \frac{(3^{2 \times 1^{84}})}{(75 + (0 - (9 \times 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{3^{2+1+8-4}}{7 + 5096} &:= \frac{(3 + (2 + (1 + 84)))}{(7 \times (5 \times ((0 \times 9) + 6)))} &:= \frac{(3 + (218 + 4))}{(7 \times (5 \times (0 + (9 + 6))))} \\ &:= \frac{(32 + (1 + 84))}{(7 \times ((5 \times (0 + 9)) - 6))} &:= \frac{(32 + (18 + 4))}{((7 + (5 - (0 - 9))) \times 6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{46712}{58390} &:= \frac{((4 + (6 \times (7 \times 1))) \times 2)}{((5 \times (8 - 3)) + 90)} &:= \frac{((4 + (6 + (7 - 1))) \times 2)}{(5 + (8 + (3 \times (9 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(4 - (6 - (71 \times 2)))}{(5 \times (8 + (3 \times (9 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (((6 \times 7) + 1) \times 2))}{((5 \times 8) + 390)} &:= \frac{(4 \times ((6 \times 7) + (1 + 2)))}{(5 \times ((8 - 3) \times (9 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 - (7 - (1 + 2))))}{(5 \times (8 + (3 - (9 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 \times ((7 + 1) \times 2)))}{(5 \times (8 \times (3 + (9 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 \times ((7 - 1)^2))}{(5 \times (8 \times (3 \times (9 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 \times (7 \times (1^2))))}{((5 \times (8 \times 3)) + 90)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 \times (7 + 12)))}{(5 \times ((8 \times 3) + 90))} &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 + ((7 - 1) \times 2))}{(5 - (8 - (3 + 90)))} &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 + (7 \times (1 \times 2))))}{(5 + (8 - (3 - 90)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 + (7 + (1 \times 2))))}{(5 \times ((8 \times 3) - (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times (6 + (7 + (1^2))))}{(5 \times (8 - (3 - (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 \times (67 - (1 \times 2)))}{((5 \times 83) - 90)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (6 \times (7 - (1^2))))}{(5 + ((8 - 3) \times (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 + (6 + (7 - (1^2))))}{(5 + ((8 \times 3) - (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 + (6 + (7 \times (1 \times 2))))}{((5 \times (8 \times 3)) - 90)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (6 + (7 + (1 + 2))))}{(5^{8+3-9+0})} := \frac{(4 + (67 - (1 + 2)))}{(58 + (3 \times (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 + 6712)}{(5 + 8390)} \\
 &:= \frac{(46 \times (7 + (1^2)))}{(5 \times (83 + (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(46 + (71 \times 2))}{(5 \times (8 + (39 - 0)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{53928}{67410}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((5^3) + 9) \times (2 \times 8))}{(67 \times (4 \times 10))} := \frac{(((5 + 3) \times (9^2)) - 8)}{((6 + 74) \times 10)} := \frac{(((5 - 3) \times 9) - (2 - 8))}{((6 - (7 - 4)) \times 10)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((5 - 3)^9) + (2 \times 8))}{(6 \times ((7 + 4) \times 10))} := \frac{(((5 - 3)^9) + 28)}{(674 + (1 - 0))} := \frac{((5 - ((3 - 9) \times 2)) \times 8)}{((6 + (7 + 4)) \times 10)} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 - (3 - (9 - 2))) \times 8)}{(6 + (74 + 10))} := \frac{((5^3) - ((9^2) + 8))}{((6 \times 7) + (4 - (1 - 0)))} := \frac{((5^3) - (9 - 28))}{(6 \times ((7 - 4) \times 10))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 + (3 \times (9 + 2))) \times 8)}{(((6 \times 7) - 4) \times 10)} := \frac{((5 + (39 + 2)) \times 8)}{(((6 \times 7) + 4) \times 10)} := \frac{((5 - 3) \times (9 \times 28))}{((67 - 4) \times 10)} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 - 3) \times (92 - 8))}{(6 \times (7 \times (4 + (1 - 0))))} := \frac{((53 + (9 \times 2)) \times 8)}{((67 + 4) \times 10)} := \frac{(5 - (3 - ((9 \times 2) + 8)))}{(6 + ((7 \times 4) + (1 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 - (3 \times (9 - (2 + 8))))}{(6 + (7 - (4 - (1 - 0))))} := \frac{(5 - (3 + (9 \times (2 - 8))))}{(6 + (74 - 10))} := \frac{(5 + ((3 \times 9) + (2 \times 8)))}{(6 \times (7 + (4 - (1 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + ((3 \times 9) - 28))}{(6 - (7 + (4 - 10)))} := \frac{(5 + (3 \times ((9^2) + 8)))}{((6 + (7 \times 4)) \times 10)} := \frac{(5 + (3^{9+2-8}))}{(6 - (7 - (41 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (3 + ((9 - 2) \times 8))}{(6 + (74 \times (1 - 0)))} := \frac{(53 + (9 - (2 + 8)))}{((6 \times (7 + 4)) - (1 - 0))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{59328}{74160}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((5 \times 9) + 3) \times 28)}{(7 \times (4 \times (1 \times 60)))} := \frac{(((5 + (9 \times 3)) \times 2) - 8)}{(7 + (4 - (1 - 60)))} := \frac{((5 \times (9 - (3^2))) + 8)}{(7 + (4 - (1^6 + 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 \times (9 - (3 + 2))) + 8)}{(7 \times (4 + (1^6 + 0)))} := \frac{((5 \times (9 - (3 + 2))) - 8)}{((7 \times (4 - 1)) - (6 - 0))} := \frac{((5 \times (9 - (3 - 2))) + 8)}{((7 + (4 - 1)) \times (6 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 \times (9 + 3)) + (2 \times 8))}{((7 \times (4 + 1)) + 60)} := \frac{((5 + (9 - (3 \times 2))) \times 8)}{(74 + (1 \times (6 - 0)))} := \frac{((5 + (9 - (3 + 2))) \times 8)}{(74 + (16 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 + (9 \times (3 - 2))) \times 8)}{(7 \times (4 + (16 - 0)))} := \frac{((5 + 9) \times ((3 \times 2) + 8))}{(7 \times (41 - (6 - 0)))} := \frac{((5 + 9) \times ((3^2) \times 8))}{(7 \times ((4 - 1) \times 60))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 + 9) \times (32 \times 8))}{(7 \times (4 \times 160))} := \frac{((5 - 93) \times (2 - 8))}{((7 + (4 \times 1)) \times 60)} := \frac{(5 - (9 - ((3 - 2) \times 8)))}{(7 + (4 - (1 \times (6 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 - (9 - (32 - 8)))}{(7 + ((4 - 1) \times (6 - 0)))} := \frac{(5 - (93 - (2^8)))}{(7 \times ((4 + 1) \times (6 - 0)))} := \frac{(5 \times ((9 + 3) \times 28))}{(7 \times ((4 + 1) \times 60))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times ((9 - 3) \times (2 \times 8)))}{((7 + (4 - 1)) \times 60)} := \frac{(5 \times (9 - (3 + (2 - 8))))}{(74 + (1^6 + 0))} := \frac{(5 \times 9 \times ((3 - 2) \times 8))}{((74 + 1) \times (6 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times (9 \times (32 \times 8)))}{(((7^4) - 1) \times (6 - 0))} := \frac{(5 + (93 + (2 + 8)))}{(74 + (1 + 60))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{5403}{172896}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((5 - (4 - 0)) \times 3)}{(1 - (7 + (2 - (8 + 96))))} := \frac{((5 \times (4 - 0)) + 3)}{(1 \times (7 + ((2 - (8 - 9))^6)))} := \frac{((5 + (4 - 0)) \times 3)}{(1 \times ((72 + (8 \times 9)) \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 + 40) \times 3)}{((1 + (728 - 9)) \times 6)} := \frac{(5 - (4 - (0 \times 3)))}{(1 \times (7 + (2 + (8 + (9 + 6))))} := \frac{(5 - (4 \times (0 - 3)))}{(1 + (7 + (2 + (89 \times 6))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(5 - (4 + (0 - 3)))}{(1 + ((7 \times (2 + (8 + 9))) - 6))} := \frac{(5 \times (4 - (0 \times 3)))}{((1 + 7) \times (2 + ((8 \times 9) + 6)))} := \frac{(5 \times (4 - (0 - 3)))}{(1 \times (7 \times ((2^8) - 96)))} \\
 & := \frac{(5 \times (4 \times (0 + 3)))}{((1 + 7) \times (2 \times (8 \times (9 + 6))))} := \frac{(5^{4-03})}{(1 - (7 - (2 \times (89 - 6))))} := \frac{(5 + (4 - (0 \times 3)))}{((1 - (7 + ((2 - 8) \times 9))) \times 6)} \\
 & := \frac{(5 + (4 - (0 - 3)))}{((1 - (7 + (2 - (8 \times 9)))) \times 6)} := \frac{(5 + (4^{03}))}{(1 \times ((7 + (2 \times 8)) \times 96))} := \frac{(5 + (4 + (0 - 3)))}{(1 + (7 + ((2 \times 89) + 6)))} \\
 & := \frac{(5 + (40 + 3))}{((17 \times ((2 + 8) \times 9)) + 6)} := \frac{(5 + (40 - 3))}{((1 + (7 - (2 - 8))) \times 96)} := \frac{(5 + 403)}{(17 \times ((2^8) \times (9 - 6)))} \\
 & := \frac{(54 - (0 \times 3))}{(1 - (7 - (289 \times 6)))} := \frac{(54 - (0 - 3))}{(1728 + 96)} := \frac{(54 \times (0 + 3))}{(1728 \times (9 - 6))} \\
 & := \frac{(54^{03})}{(((1 + (7 - 2))^8) \times (9 - 6))} := \frac{(54 + (0 - 3))}{(1 \times ((7 + ((2^8) + 9)) \times 6))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{6537}{209184}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(((6 + 5) \times 3) + 7)}{(20 \times ((9 - (1 - 8)) \times 4))} := \frac{(((6 - 5)^3) + 7)}{2^{09-184}} := \frac{((6 - (5 - 3)) \times 7)}{((20 + (9 - 1)) \times (8 \times 4))} \\
 & := \frac{((6 \times (5 - 3)) + 7)}{(((2 \times (0 + 9)) + 1) \times (8 \times 4))} := \frac{((6 \times 5) - (3 \times 7))}{((2^{09-1}) + (8 \times 4))} := \frac{((6^{5-3}) - 7)}{((20 + (9 \times 1)) \times (8 \times 4))} \\
 & := \frac{((6 - 5) \times (3 + 7))}{((2 \times (0 + (9 \times 18))) - 4)} := \frac{(6 - (5 - (3 + 7)))}{((2 - (0 - (9 \times 1))) \times (8 \times 4))} := \frac{(6 - (5 \times (3 - 7)))}{(((20 \times (9 + 1)) + 8) \times 4)} \\
 & := \frac{(6 - (5 + (3 - 7)))}{(2 - (0 - ((9 \times 18) - 4)))} := \frac{(6 \times (5 \times (3^7)))}{(20 \times ((9 + (1 + 8))^4))} := \frac{(6^{5 \times 3 - 7})}{(2 \times (0 + ((9 \times (1 \times 8))^4)))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 + ((5 + 3) \times 7))}{(2 \times (0 + ((9 - 1) \times (8 + 4))))} := \frac{(6 + ((5 + 3) \times 7))}{((20 \times (91 + 8)) + 4)} := \frac{(6 + ((5 - 3) \times 7))}{(2 \times (0 + ((9 + 1) \times (8 \times 4))))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 + (5 - (3 + 7)))}{2^{09-1 \times 8 + 4}} := \frac{(6 + (5 - (3 - 7)))}{((2^{09 \times 1}) - (8 \times 4))} := \frac{(6 + (5 \times (3 \times 7)))}{((20 + 91) \times (8 \times 4))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 + (5 + (3 \times 7)))}{((2^{09-18}) \times 4)} := \frac{(6 + (5 + (3 + 7)))}{(((20 \times (9 - 1)) + 8) \times 4)} := \frac{(6 + (5 + (3 - 7)))}{((2^{09-1}) - (8 \times 4))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 + (53 - 7))}{((20 \times (91 - 8)) + 4)} := \frac{(65 + (3 + 7))}{(20 \times ((9 + 1) \times (8 + 4)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{6894}{172350}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(((6 + 8) \times 9) - 4)}{(((1 + 7)^2) - 3) \times 50} := \frac{((6 - (8 - 9)) \times 4)}{((1 + (7 + (2 \times 3))) \times 50)} := \frac{((6 \times (8 + 9)) + 4)}{((1 + ((7^2) + 3)) \times 50)} \\
 & := \frac{((6 \times 8) - (9 \times 4))}{(1 \times ((7 + (2 - 3)) \times 50))} := \frac{((6 \times 8) - (9 + 4))}{((172 + 3) \times (5 - 0))} := \frac{((6 \times 8) + (9 \times 4))}{(1 \times (7 \times (2 \times (3 \times 50))))} \\
 & := \frac{((6 + 8) \times (9 - 4))}{(1 \times (7 \times ((2 + 3) \times 50)))} := \frac{(6 - ((8 - 9) \times 4))}{(1 - (7 - (2^{3+5-0})))} := \frac{(6 - (8 - (9 \times 4)))}{((1 - (7 - 23)) \times 50)} \\
 & := \frac{(6 - (8 - (9 - 4)))}{(1 \times ((7 + (2^3)) \times (5 - 0)))} := \frac{(6 - (8 - 94))}{(1 \times (((7^2) - 3) \times 50))} := \frac{(6 \times (8 - (9 - 4)))}{((1 + (7 - (2 - 3))) \times 50)} \\
 & := \frac{(6 \times (8 + (9 + 4)))}{(1 \times ((7 + 2) \times 350))} := \frac{(6 + ((8 + 9) \times 4))}{(((17 \times 2) + 3) \times 50)} := \frac{(6 + ((8 - 9) \times 4))}{(1 + (7 - ((2^3) - 50)))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 + (8 - (9 + 4)))}{(1 + (7 + (2 + (3 \times (5 - 0))))} := \frac{(6 + (8 - (9 - 4)))}{((1 + (7 \times 2)) \times (3 \times (5 - 0)))} := \frac{(6 + (8 \times (9 \times 4)))}{(1 \times ((7^2) \times (3 \times 50)))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 + (8 \times (9 + 4)))}{(1 + (((7 \times 2)^3) + (5 - 0)))} := \frac{(6 + (8 \times (9 - 4)))}{((17 + (2 \times 3)) \times 50)} := \frac{(6 + (8 + (9 \times 4)))}{((17 + (2^3)) \times 50)} \\
 & := \frac{(68 - (9 \times 4))}{((1 + (7 + (2^3))) \times 50)} := \frac{(68 + (9 \times 4))}{(1 \times (((7^2) + 3) \times 50))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9102}{345876} &:= \frac{((9 - (1 - 0)) \times 2)}{((3^4) + (5 + (87 \times 6)))} := \frac{((9 - (1 - 0))^2)}{((3 - (4 - 5)) \times (8 \times 76))} := \frac{((9 + (1 - 0)) \times 2)}{((3 + (4 - (5 - 8))) \times 76)} \\
 &:= \frac{((9 + (1 - 0))^2)}{(((3^4) - 5) \times (8 + (7 \times 6)))} := \frac{((9 + 10) \times 2)}{(((3 \times (4 + 5)) - 8) \times 76)} := \frac{(9 - (1 - (0 - 2)))}{((3 \times (4 + 58)) + (7 \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 - (1 + (0 - 2)))}{(3 + (((45 + 8) \times 7) + 6))} := \frac{(9 - (10 - 2))}{(3 - (4 - (5 - (8 - (7 \times 6))))))} := \frac{(9 \times (1 - (0 - 2)))}{(3 + ((4^5) - ((8 - 7)^6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 \times (1 \times (0 + 2)))}{(3 \times (4 \times (58 - (7 - 6))))} := \frac{(9 \times (10 \times 2))}{(((3^4) - 5) \times ((8 + 7) \times 6))} := \frac{(9 \times (10 - 2))}{((3 \times (4^5)) - (8 \times (7 \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 \times (1 \times (0 + 2)))}{((3 \times (4^{5 \times (8 - 7)})) + 6)} := \frac{((3 + 45) \times 8) - (7 \times 6)}{(9 \times (10^2))} := \frac{(9 + (1 - (0 - 2)))}{(((3^4) - (5 \times (8 - 7))) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 + (1 + (0 - 2)))}{((3 + (4 + (5 - 8))) \times 76)} := \frac{(9 + (10 + 2))}{(3 \times ((4 \times (58 + 7)) + 6))} := \frac{(9 + (10 - 2))}{(((3^4) + 5) \times 8) - (7 \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 + 102)}{(91 \times (0 + 2))} := \frac{(91 - (0 \times 2))}{(3458 \times (7 - 6))} := \frac{(91 - (0 - 2))}{(3458 + 76)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((3 \times (4 \times 58)) + 7) \times 6)}{(91 \times (0 + 2))} := \frac{(91 + (0 - 2))}{(3458 - 76)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9862}{345170} &:= \frac{(((9 + 8) \times 6) - 2)}{((3 - (4 - 51)) \times 70)} := \frac{(((9 - 8)^6) \times 2)}{((3 \times (4 - (5 - 1))) + 70)} := \frac{(((9 - 8)^6) + 2)}{(((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 1)) + 70)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((9 - 8) \times 6) \times 2)}{(((3 \times 4) - (5 \times 1)) \times 70)} := \frac{(((9 \times (8 - 6)) - 2)}{((9 \times 8) + (6 + 2))} := \frac{(3 \times (4 \times (5 + 170)))}{((9 \times 8) + (6 - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((3 \times 4) - (5 \times 1)) \times 70)}{((9 \times 8) + (6 \times 2))} := \frac{(((3 \times 4) - (5 - 1)) \times 70)}{((9 \times 8) + (6 + 2))} := \frac{(3 \times (4 \times (5 + 170)))}{((9 \times 8) + (6 - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 + 4) \times ((5 + 1) \times 70))}{((9 \times 8) - 62)} := \frac{((34 + (5 + 1)) \times 70)}{((9 + (8 \times 6)) \times 2)} := \frac{((34 + (5 - 1)) \times 70)}{((9 + (8 + 6)) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 - (4 - 51)) \times (7 - 0))}{((9 + (8 - 6)) \times 2)} := \frac{(3 \times (((4 \times 5) - 1) \times 70))}{((9 + 8) \times (6 - 2))} := \frac{((3 + (4 \times (5 \times 1))) \times 70)}{((9 - 8) \times (6 \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 + (4 + (5 - 1))) \times 70)}{((9 - 8) \times (6 + 2))} := \frac{(((3 + 4) \times 5) - 1) \times 70}{((9 - 8) \times (6 - 2))} := \frac{(3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (1 \times (7 - 0))))}{((9 - 8)^{6-2})} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 - (4 - (5 \times 1))) \times 70)}{(9 - (8 - (6 - 2)))} := \frac{((3 + (4 - (5 \times 1))) \times 70)}{(9 \times ((8 \times 6) - 2))} := \frac{(3 + (4 + ((5 - 1) \times (7 - 0))))}{(9 \times (8 - (6 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(345 - 170)}{(9 \times (8 + (6 + 2)))} := \frac{(3 + (4 \times 51)) \times 70}{(98 - (6 - 2))} := \frac{(((3 \times 4) + (5 + 1)) \times 70)}{((3 \times (4 \times ((5 + 1) \times 70)))} := \frac{(3 + (45 - 1)) \times 70}{((3 + (45 - 1)) \times 70)}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.23 24 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18964}{23705} &:= \frac{(((1 + 8) \times 9) - 6) \times 4}{((2 + (3 + 70)) \times 5)} := \frac{(((1 - (8 - 9))^6) - 4)}{(((2^3) + (7 - 0)) \times 5)} := \frac{((1 - (8 - (9 + 6))) \times 4)}{(2 + (3 - (7 \times (0 - 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (8 - (9 + (6 + 4))))}{((2 \times (3 + (7 - 0))) - 5)} := \frac{(1 - (8 - (9 + (6 - 4))))}{(2 + (3 - (7 \times (0 \times 5))))} := \frac{(1 - (8 + (9 - 64)))}{((2 + (3 + (7 - 0))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (((8 \times 9) + 6) \times 4))}{(2 \times (3 \times (70 - 5)))} := \frac{(1 \times ((8 + (9 + 6)) \times 4))}{((2 + (3 \times (7 - 0))) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 \times ((8 + 96) \times 4))}{((2^3) \times (70 - 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((89 - 6) \times 4))}{((2 \times (3 \times 70)) - 5)} := \frac{(1 \times (8 \times ((9 + 6) \times 4))}{((2^3) \times (70 + 5))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (9 - (6 - 4))))}{(2 + (3 + (70 - 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (9 + 64)))}{(2 \times ((3 + 70) \times 5))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 + (9 \times (6 \times 4))))}{((2^3) \times (7 \times (0 + 5)))} := \frac{(1 + (8 - (9 - (6 \times 4))))}{(2 \times (3 + (7 - (0 - 5))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(1 + (8 - (9 - 64)))}{(2 + (3 + (70 + 5)))} := \frac{(1 + (8 + (9 - (6 + 4))))}{(2 \times (3 + (7 + (0 - 5))))} := \frac{(1 + (8 + (9 - (6 - 4))))}{(2 \times (3 + (7 - (0 \times 5))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (8 + (9 + (6 + 4))))}{(23 + (7 - (0 - 5)))} := \frac{(1 + (8 + (9 + (6 - 4))))}{((2 \times (3 + (7 - 0))) + 5)} := \frac{(1 + (89 - (6 + 4)))}{(2 \times ((3 + (7 - 0)) \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(18 + ((9 \times 6) + 4))}{((2 - (3 \times 7)) \times (0 - 5))} := \frac{1896 + 4}{2370 + 5} := \frac{1896 - 4}{2370 - 5} \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{63152}{78940} := \frac{(((6 - (3 - 1)) \times 5)^2)}{((7 \times (8 \times 9)) - (4 - 0))} := \frac{((6 - (3 \times 1)) \times 52)}{((7 + 8) \times (9 + (4 - 0)))} := \frac{((6 - (3 - 1)) \times 52)}{(((7 \times 8) + 9) \times (4 - 0))}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{((6 \times (3 \times (1 \times 5))) + 2)}{((7 \times (8 + 9)) - (4 - 0))} := \frac{((6 \times (3 + (1 + 5))) - 2)}{(78 - (9 + (4 - 0)))} := \frac{((6^{3 \times 1^5}) \times 2)}{((7 + 8) \times (9 \times (4 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{((6^3) + (1 + (5 + 2)))}{(7 \times (8 \times (9 - (4 - 0))))} := \frac{((6 + ((3 - 1) \times 5))^2)}{((7 - (8 - 9)) \times 40)} := \frac{((6 + ((3 - 1)^5)) \times 2)}{(((7 + 8) \times 9) - 40)} \\ &:= \frac{((6 + (3 - 1)) \times (5 \times 2))}{(7 + (89 + (4 - 0)))} := \frac{((63 + 1) \times (5 - 2))}{((7 + (8 - 9)) \times 40)} := \frac{(6 - (3 - (1 \times (5^2))))}{(7 - (8 - (9 \times (4 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times ((3 - 1) \times (5^2)))}{(7 + (8 + (9 \times 40)))} := \frac{(6 \times ((3 - 1)^{5+2}))}{((7 + (8 + 9)) \times 40)} := \frac{(6 \times ((31 - 5) \times 2))}{(78 \times (9 - (4 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times (3 + (1^{5^2})))}{(7 - (8 + (9 - 40)))} := \frac{(6 \times (3 + (15 + 2)))}{((7 \times 8) + (94 - 0))} := \frac{(6 \times (31 + (5 - 2)))}{(7 - (8 \times (9 - 40)))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + (3 - (1^{5^2})))}{(7 + (8 - (9 - (4 - 0))))} := \frac{(6 + (3 - (1 - 52)))}{(7 + ((8 + 9) \times (4 - 0)))} := \frac{(6 + (3 \times (1 + (5^2))))}{((7 \times 8) + (9 + 40))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + (3 + (1 \times (5 + 2))))}{(7 + (8 + (9 - (4 - 0))))} := \frac{(6 + (3 + (1 + (5 \times 2))))}{((7 \times 8) + (9 - 40))} := \frac{(631 - (5 - 2))}{(789 - (4 - 0))} \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{73264}{91580} := \frac{(((7 - (3 + 2))^6) + 4)}{(9 + (1 - (5 - 80)))} := \frac{(((7^3) \times 2) - (6 - 4))}{(9 \times (15 + 80))} := \frac{(((7 + (3^2)) \times 6) + 4)}{((9 \times (1 \times 5)) + 80)}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(((7 + (3 - 2)) \times 6) - 4)}{((9 \times 15) - 80)} := \frac{(((7 \times (3 \times (2 \times 6))) + 4)}{((9 - (1 \times 5)) \times 80)} := \frac{(((7 \times (3 \times (2 + 6))) + 4)}{((9 \times 15) + 80)} \\ &:= \frac{((7 \times 32) + 64)}{(9 \times (1 \times (5 \times (8 - 0))))} := \frac{(((7 + (3 \times (2^6))) \times 4)}{(915 + 80)} := \frac{(((7 + (3 \times 2)) \times 64)}{((9 - (1 - 5)) \times 80)} \\ &:= \frac{((7 + (3 - 2)) \times (6 \times 4))}{((9 - (1 + 5)) \times 80)} := \frac{((7 + (3 - 2)) \times 64)}{((9 - (1^5)) \times 80)} := \frac{((7 + 3) \times ((2^6) \times 4))}{((9 - 1) \times (5 \times 80))} \\ &:= \frac{((7 + 3) \times ((2^6) + 4))}{((9 + 1) \times (5 + 80))} := \frac{((7 + 3) \times ((2 + 6) \times 4))}{((9 + (1 - 5)) \times 80)} := \frac{((7 + 3) \times (26 + 4))}{((91 \times 5) - 80)} \\ &:= \frac{((7 - 3) \times (2 + (6 \times 4)))}{((9 + 1) \times (5 + (8 - 0)))} := \frac{(7 - (3 - ((2^6) - 4)))}{((9 + (1^5)) \times (8 - 0))} := \frac{(7 - (3 - (2 - (6 - 4))))}{(9 - (1 - (5 - (8 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 - (3 - (2^{6-4})))}{(9 + ((1^5)^8 + 0))} := \frac{(7 + (3 - (2 - (6 \times 4))))}{((9 + (1 - 5)) \times (8 - 0))} := \frac{(7 + (3 - (2 - 64)))}{(9 + ((1^5) + 80))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + (3 + (2 + 64)))}{(9 + (1 + (5 + 80)))} := \frac{(7 + (3 + (26 + 4)))}{(9 + (1 + (5 \times (8 - 0))))} := \frac{(732 - 64)}{(915 - 80)} \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{2973}{148650} := \frac{(((2 \times 9) + 7)^3)}{(((1 - (4 - 8))^6) \times 50)} := \frac{((2 \times 9) + (7 + 3))}{(14 \times ((8 - 6) \times 50))} := \frac{((2 \times 9) + 73)}{((1 + (4 + 86)) \times 50)}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{((2^9) - (7^3))}{((1 + (4 + 8)) \times 650)} := \frac{((2 + (9 + 7)) \times 3)}{(1 \times ((48 + 6) \times 50))} := \frac{((29 + 7)^3)}{(((14 - 8)^6) \times 50)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(2 - (9 - (7 \times 3)))}{((1^4) \times ((8 + 6) \times 50))} := \frac{(2 - (9 - (7 + 3)))}{((1 + (4 - (8 - 6))) \times 50)} := \frac{(2 \times ((9 \times 7) + 3))}{((14 + 8) \times (6 \times 50))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((9 - 7) \times 3))}{((14 - (8 - 6)) \times 50)} := \frac{(2 \times ((9 - 7)^3))}{(1 \times ((4^{8-6}) \times 50))} := \frac{(2 \times (9 - (7 - 3)))}{((14 + 86) \times (5 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (9 \times (7 - 3)))}{(1 \times ((4 + 8) \times (6 \times 50)))} := \frac{(2 \times (9 + (7 - 3)))}{(1 \times (((4 \times 8) - 6) \times 50))} := \frac{(2 + ((9 \times 7) - 3))}{((14 + (8 \times 6)) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + ((9 - 7) \times 3))}{(1 \times (4 \times ((8 - 6) \times 50)))} := \frac{(2 + (9 - (7 + 3)))}{((1^{486}) \times 50)} := \frac{(2 + (9 - (7 - 3)))}{(1 + ((4 \times 86) + (5 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (9 \times (7 - 3)))}{(1 \times (((4 \times 8) + 6) \times 50))} := \frac{(2 + (9 + (7 - 3)))}{(((1^4) + (8 + 6)) \times 50)} := \frac{(29 - (7 + 3))}{((1 + (4 + (8 + 6))) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{(29 - (7 - 3))}{((1 - ((4 - 8) \times 6)) \times 50)} := \frac{(29 + (7 + 3))}{((1 + ((4 \times 8) + 6)) \times 50)} := \frac{(297 - 3)}{((1 + 48) \times (6 \times 50))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{7269}{145380}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((7 \times 2) - 6) \times 9)}{((1 + ((4 \times 5) - 3)) \times 80)} := \frac{(((7 \times 2) + (6 \times 9)))}{((1 + (4^{5-3})) \times 80)} := \frac{(((7 \times 2) + (6 + 9)))}{(1 \times ((4 \times (5^3)) + 80))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 \times 2) + (6 - 9))}{(1 \times (4 \times (5 \times (3 + (8 - 0)))))} := \frac{((7 \times 2) + 69)}{(1 \times (4 \times (5 \times (3 + 80))))} := \frac{((7^2) - (6 - 9))}{((1 + (4 + (5^3))) \times (8 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7^2) + (6 + 9))}{(1 \times ((4^{5-3}) \times 80))} := \frac{((7^2) + (6 - 9))}{(((1 + (4 + 5))^3) - 80)} := \frac{((7 + (2 \times 6)) \times 9)}{(1 \times ((4 + 5) \times 380))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 - ((2 \times 6) - 9))}{((1^{453}) \times 80)} := \frac{(7 - (2 - (6 + 9)))}{((1 - (4 - 53)) \times (8 - 0))} := \frac{(7 - (2 - (6 - 9)))}{(1 \times (4 \times (5 - (3 - (8 - 0)))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 - (2 \times (6 - 9)))}{(1 \times (4 + ((5 - 3)^8 + 0)))} := \frac{(7 - (2 + (6 - 9)))}{(1 \times ((4 - (5 - 3)) \times 80))} := \frac{(7 \times ((2 \times 6) - 9))}{(1 + (4 + (5 \times (3 + 80))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 \times ((2 + 6) \times 9))}{(((1^4) + (5^3)) \times 80)} := \frac{(7 + ((2 \times 6) + 9))}{((1 + (4 + (5 - 3))) \times 80)} := \frac{(7 + ((2 \times 6) - 9))}{(((1 + 4)^{5-3}) \times (8 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + ((2^6) + 9))}{((1 + (4 + (5 \times 3))) \times 80)} := \frac{(7 + (2 - (6 - 9)))}{(1 + (4 - (5 - (3 \times 80))))} := \frac{(7 + (2 \times (6 - 9)))}{(1 \times (4 + (5 + (3 + (8 - 0)))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (2 + (6 + 9)))}{(1 \times (4 \times (5 \times (3 \times (8 - 0)))))} := \frac{(7 + (2 + (6 - 9)))}{((14 \times (5 + 3)) + (8 - 0))} := \frac{(72 - 69)}{(1 + (4 + (5 \times (3 + (8 - 0)))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{7938}{254016}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((7 + 9) \times 3) + 8)}{(2^5) \times (40 + 16)} := \frac{(7 + 9)^3 \times 8}{2^{5 \times 4 + 0 \times 16}} := \frac{(((7 - 9) \times 3) + 8)}{2^{5-4+0-1+6}} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 - (9 - 3)) \times 8)}{2^{5+4+0-1^6}} := \frac{(7 - 9 + 3)^8}{2^5 + 4 \times 0 \times 16} := \frac{((7 \times (9 - 3)) + 8)}{(25 \times (4 \times (0 + 16)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 \times (9 - 3)) - 8)}{((2 \times (540 + 1)) + 6)} := \frac{((7 \times 9) - (3 \times 8))}{((7 \times 9) - (3 \times 8))} := \frac{((7 \times 9) + 38)}{((2 + (5 \times 40)) \times 16)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 \times 9) - 38)}{(2 \times (5 + (401 - 6)))} := \frac{((7 + 93) \times 8)}{(25 \times (4^{-01+6}))} := \frac{((7 - 9) \times (3 - 8))}{(2 + ((54 + (0 - 1)) \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 - (9 - (3 + 8)))}{((2 + (5 + (40 + 1))) \times 6)} := \frac{(7 - (9 + (3 - 8)))}{(2 \times ((5 + (4 + (0 - 1))) \times 6))} := \frac{(7 - (9 - 38))}{(((2^5) + 40) \times 16)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 \times (9 + (3 + 8)))}{(7 \times (9 + (3 + 8)))} := \frac{(7 \times (9 + (3 - 8)))}{(7 \times (9 + (3 - 8)))} := \frac{(7 + ((9 \times 3) - 8))}{(7 + ((9 \times 3) - 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + 5) \times (40 \times 16)}{(7 + (9 - (3 + 8)))} := \frac{(2 + (54 - 0)) \times 16}{(7 + (9 - (3 - 8)))} := \frac{(2 - 54) \times (0 - 16)}{(7 + (9 + (3 \times 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^5) \times (4 - (0 - (1^6))))}{(7 + (9 + (3 - 8)))} := \frac{((2^5) + (40 \times 16))}{(7 + (9 + 38))} := \frac{((2^5) \times (40 \times (1^6)))}{(79 - 38)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (9 + (3 - 8)))}{((2 + (5 \times (4 - 0))) \times 16)} := \frac{(7 + (9 + 38))}{(2 \times (54 \times (0 + 16)))} := \frac{(79 - 38)}{((2^5) \times (40 + (1^6)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{8469}{127035}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((8 \times 4) - 6) \times 9)}{((1 - (2 - 703)) \times 5)} := \frac{((8 \times (4 + 6)) + 9)}{(1 \times ((270 - 3) \times 5))} := \frac{((8 \times (4 + 6)) - 9)}{((1 + (2 + (70 \times 3))) \times 5)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{((8 \times 4) - (6 + 9))}{(1 \times (270 - (3 \times 5)))} & := \frac{((8 \times 4) - (6 - 9))}{((1 + (2 \times (7 - 0))) \times 35)} & := \frac{((8 \times 4) + (6 - 9))}{(((12 \times (7 - 0)) + 3) \times 5)} \\
 & \frac{((8 + (4 + 6)) \times 9)}{((1 + (2 + (7 - 0))) \times (3^5))} & \frac{(8 - ((4 - 6) \times 9))}{(1 + (((2^7 + 0) \times 3) + 5))} & \frac{(8 - (4 - (6 + 9)))}{(1 \times (270 + (3 \times 5)))} \\
 & \frac{(8 - (4 - (6 - 9)))}{(1 + (2 \times (7 - (0 \times 35))))} & \frac{(8 - (4 + (6 - 9)))}{((1 + (2 \times (7 - (0 - 3)))) \times 5)} & \frac{(8 - (4 - 69))}{((1 + (2 + 70)) \times (3 \times 5))} \\
 & \frac{(8^{4+6-9})}{((1 + (2 - (7 \times (0 - 3)))) \times 5)} & \frac{(8 + ((4 \times 6) + 9))}{((1 + 2) \times ((70 \times 3) - 5))} & \frac{(8 + ((4 \times 6) - 9))}{(1 \times ((2 + (70 - 3)) \times 5))} \\
 & \frac{(8 + (4 - (6 - 9)))}{((1 + (2 \times (7 - 0))) \times (3 \times 5))} & \frac{(8 + (4 \times (6 + 9)))}{(12 \times (70 + (3 \times 5)))} & \frac{(8 + (4 + (6 + 9)))}{(1 \times (27 \times (0 + (3 \times 5))))} \\
 & \frac{(8 + (4 + (6 - 9)))}{(1 \times ((2 + (7 - 0)) \times (3 \times 5)))} & \frac{(8 + (4 + 69))}{(1 \times ((2 - 7) \times (0 - (3^5))))} & \frac{(8 + (46 + 9))}{(1 \times (27 \times (0 + 35)))} \\
 & \frac{(8 + (46 - 9))}{((1 + (2 \times (70 - 3))) \times 5)} & \frac{(84 - (6 + 9))}{((1 - (2 - 70)) \times (3 \times 5))} & \frac{(84 - (6 - 9))}{(1270 + 35)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{9172}{403568}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{((9 - (1^7)) \times 2)}{(4 \times (0 + ((3 \times 56) + 8)))} & := \frac{((9 - (1 + 7)) \times 2)}{(4 \times (0 + (3 + (5 + (6 + 8)))))} & := \frac{((9 - (1 - 7)) \times 2)}{(40 \times (35 + (6 - 8)))} \\
 & \frac{((9 \times (1 + 7)) + 2)}{((40 - 3) \times ((5 + 6) \times 8))} & \frac{((9 + (1 \times 7)) \times 2)}{((4^{03}) \times ((5 \times 6) - 8))} & \frac{((9 + (1^7)) \times 2)}{(40 \times (3 + (5 + (6 + 8))))} \\
 & \frac{((9 - 1) \times (7 + 2))}{((40 + 356) \times 8)} & \frac{(9 - ((1^7) + 2))}{(4 \times (0 + (3 - (5 - 68))))} & \frac{(9 - ((1 - 7) \times 2))}{((4 \times (0 + (3^5))) - (6 \times 8))} \\
 & \frac{(9 - (1 - (7 \times 2)))}{(((40 \times 3) - (5 - 6)) \times 8)} & \frac{(9 - (1 - (7 - 2)))}{(4 - ((0 \times 3) - 568))} & \frac{(9 - (1 \times (7 - 2)))}{(((4^{-03+5}) + 6) \times 8)} \\
 & \frac{(9 - (1^{72}))}{((4 \times (0 + (3 \times (5 \times 6)))) - 8)} & \frac{(9 - (1 + (7 - 2)))}{(4 \times (0 - (35 - 68)))} & \frac{(9 \times (1^{72}))}{(403 - (5 - (6 - 8)))} \\
 & \frac{(9 + ((1^7) + 2))}{(((4 \times (0 + (3 \times 5))) + 6) \times 8)} & \frac{(9 + (1 - (7 + 2)))}{(4 + (0 - (3 + (5 - (6 \times 8)))))} & \frac{(9 + (1 - (7 - 2)))}{((4 \times (0 - (3 - 56))) + 8)} \\
 & \frac{(9 + (1 \times (7 + 2)))}{((40 + (3 + 56)) \times 8)} & \frac{(9 + (1 \times (7 - 2)))}{((4 - (0 - 3)) \times ((5 + 6) \times 8))} & \frac{(9 + (1^{72}))}{(40 \times (3 - ((5 - 6) \times 8)))} \\
 & \frac{(9 + (1 + (7 \times 2)))}{(4 \times (0 + (3 \times ((5 + 6) \times 8))))} & \frac{(9 + (1 + 72))}{((40 \times (3 \times (5 \times 6))) + 8)} & \frac{(91 - (7 - 2))}{((40 + 3) \times ((5 + 6) \times 8))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{9267}{185340}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(((9 \times 2) - 6) \times 7)}{((1 + (8 + 5)) \times (3 \times 40))} & := \frac{((9 - (2 + 6))^7)}{(1 \times (8 + (5 + (3 + (4 - 0)))))} & := \frac{((9 \times 2) - (6 - 7))}{(1 \times ((8 \times 5) + 340))} \\
 & \frac{((9 \times 2) + (6 - 7))}{((1^{85}) \times 340)} & \frac{((9 \times 2) + 67)}{((1 + (8 \times 53)) \times (4 - 0))} & \frac{((9^2) - (6 + 7))}{(1 \times (8 \times (5 \times (34 - 0))))} \\
 & \frac{(9 - ((2 \times 6) - 7))}{(1 \times ((8 \times (5 \times 3)) - 40))} & \frac{(9 - (2 - (6 + 7)))}{(1 \times ((8 + (5 - 3)) \times 40))} & \frac{(9 - (2 - (6 - 7)))}{(1 + (85 + (34 - 0)))} \\
 & \frac{(9 - (2 \times (6 - 7)))}{(1 \times (8 + (53 \times (4 - 0))))} & \frac{(9 - (2 + (6 - 7)))}{(1 \times ((8 \times (5 \times 3)) + 40))} & \frac{(9 - (2 - 67))}{(1 \times (((8 \times 5) - 3) \times 40))} \\
 & \frac{(9 \times (2 - (6 - 7)))}{((1 + 8) \times (5 \times (3 \times (4 - 0))))} & \frac{(9 \times 267)}{((1 + 8) \times 5340)} & \frac{(9 + ((2 \times 6) - 7))}{(1 \times (8 \times (5 \times (3 + (4 - 0)))))} \\
 & \frac{(9 + ((2^6) + 7))}{((1 + ((8 + 5) \times 3)) \times 40)} & \frac{(9 + ((2^6) - 7))}{(1 \times (8 \times ((5^3) + 40)))} & \frac{(9 + (2 - (6 - 7)))}{(1 \times ((8 - (5 - 3)) \times 40))} \\
 & \frac{(9 + (2 \times (6 - 7)))}{((18 \times (5 + 3)) - (4 - 0))} & \frac{(9 + (2 + (6 + 7)))}{(1 \times (8 \times (5 \times (3 \times (4 - 0)))))} & \frac{(9 + (2 + 67))}{(1 \times ((8 + 5) \times (3 \times 40)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(9 + (26 - 7))}{(1 + ((8 + 5) \times (3 + 40)))} \quad := \frac{(92 - (6 \times 7))}{(1 \times (8 \times (5 + (3 \times 40))))} \quad := \frac{(92 - 67)}{((1^8) \times ((5^3) \times (4 - 0)))}$$

3.24 25 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{18940}{23675} &:= \frac{(((1^8) + 9) \times 40)}{((2^{3+6}) - (7 + 5))} &:= \frac{((1 - (8 - 9)) \times (4 - 0))}{(2 + (3 - ((6 - 7) \times 5)))} &:= \frac{((1 - (8 - 9)) \times 40)}{(2 \times (3 + ((6 \times 7) + 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{((1 - (8 - 9))^4 + 0)}{(2 - (3 \times (6 - (7 + 5))))} &:= \frac{((1 + (8 \times 9)) \times (4 - 0))}{(((2 \times 3) + 67) \times 5)} &:= \frac{((1 + (8 + 9)) \times (4 - 0))}{((2 + (3 + (6 + 7))) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + (8 + 9)) \times 40)}{(((2 + 3) \times 6)^{7-5})} &:= \frac{((1 + 8) \times (9 \times (4 - 0)))}{((2 + 3) \times (6 + 75))} &:= \frac{((1 + 8) \times (9 \times 40))}{(2 \times (3 \times 675))} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + 89) \times (4 - 0))}{(2 \times ((3 + (6 \times 7)) \times 5))} &:= \frac{((18 + 9) \times (4 - 0))}{((2 \times (3 + 67)) - 5)} &:= \frac{((18 + 9) \times 40)}{(2 \times ((3 + 6) \times 75))} \\ &:= \frac{((18 - 9) \times (4 - 0))}{((2 \times ((3 \times 6) + 7)) - 5)} &:= \frac{(1 - (8 + (9 - 40)))}{(2 \times (3 + (6 \times (7 - 5))))} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((8 \times 9) + (4 - 0)))}{((2 \times (3 + (6 \times 7))) + 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times ((8 \times 9) + 40))}{((23 \times 6) + (7 - 5))} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((8 \times 9) - 40))}{(2 - (3 - (6 + (7 \times 5))))} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((8 + 9) \times (4 - 0)))}{((2 \times (3 + (6 \times 7))) - 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (9 \times (4 - 0))))}{((2 + (3 + 67)) \times 5)} &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (9 \times 40)))}{((2^3) \times (6 \times 75))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (9 + (4 - 0))))}{(2 \times (3 + (67 - 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (9 + 40)))}{(((2^3) + 6) \times (7 \times 5))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 + (9 \times (4 - 0))))}{(((2 \times (3 + 6)) - 7) \times 5)} &:= \frac{(1 + (8 - (9 - (4 - 0))))}{(2 - (3 + (6 - (7 + 5))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (8 - (9 - 40)))}{(2 + (36 + (7 + 5)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{23184}{57960} &:= \frac{(((2^3) + 1) \times 84)}{(5 \times (7 \times (9 \times (6 - 0))))} &:= \frac{((2 \times 31) + 84)}{(5 \times (79 - (6 - 0)))} &:= \frac{((2^{3+1}) \times 84)}{(5 \times (7 \times (96 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{((2 + (3 \times (1^8))) \times 4)}{(5 \times (7 + (9 - (6 - 0))))} &:= \frac{((2 + (3 + (1 + 8))) \times 4)}{((5 \times (7 + 9)) + 60)} &:= \frac{((2 + 31) \times (8 \times 4))}{(((5 \times 7) + 9) \times 60)} \\ &:= \frac{((23 + 1) \times 84)}{((5 + 79) \times 60)} &:= \frac{(2 \times ((3 \times 18) + 4))}{(5 \times (7 - (9 - 60)))} &:= \frac{(2 \times ((3 + 18) \times 4))}{((5 - (7 - 9)) \times 60)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (3 \times (1 \times (8 \times 4))))}{(5 \times ((7 + 9) \times (6 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (3 \times (1 \times (8 + 4))))}{((5 + (7 - 9)) \times 60)} &:= \frac{(2 \times (3 \times (1 \times (8 - 4))))}{(57 + (9 - (6 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (3 \times (1 \times 84)))}{((5 + (7 + 9)) \times 60)} &:= \frac{(2 \times (3 \times (1^{84})))}{(5 + (7 + (9 - (6 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (3 + (18 \times 4)))}{((5 \times (7 \times 9)) + 60)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (3 + (18 + 4)))}{(5 - ((7 - 9) \times 60))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (31 + 84))}{((5 \times 7) + (9 \times 60))} &:= \frac{(2^{3 \times 184})}{(5 \times (7 - (9 - (6 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + ((3 - (1 - 8)) \times 4))}{(5 \times (7 \times (9 - (6 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(2 + ((3 - 1) \times 84))}{(5 \times (79 + (6 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(2 + ((31 \times 8) - 4))}{(5 \times ((7 \times 9) + 60))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (3 - (1 - (8 \times 4))))}{(5 + (79 + (6 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(2 + (3 \times (1 \times (8 + 4))))}{(5 \times (79 - 60))} &:= \frac{(2 + (3 \times (18 - 4)))}{(5 \times (7 + (9 + (6 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{2 + 3184}{5 + 7960} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{25034}{87619} := \frac{(((2 + 50) \times 3) + 4)}{(8 \times (7 + ((6 + 1) \times 9)))} := \frac{(((2 + 50) \times 3) - 4)}{((87 \times 6) + (1 + 9))} := \frac{((2 \times (5 - (0 - 3))) + 4)}{((8 - (7 - 6)) \times (1 + 9))}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (5 \times (0+3))) - 4)}{(87 - (6 - (1+9)))} := \frac{((2 \times 50) + (3 \times 4))}{(8 \times (7 \times (6 + (1^9))))} := \frac{((2^{5+0 \times 3}) + 4)}{((8 \times 7) + (61 + 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^{5+0 \times 3}) - 4)}{(((8+7) \times 6) - (1-9))} := \frac{((2^5 + 0) \times (3 + 4))}{(8 \times (7 \times (6 - (1-9))))} := \frac{((2 - 50) \times (3 - 4))}{(8 \times (7 + (6 - (1-9))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (5 \times (0 \times 34)))}{(8 - (7 - (6 \times (1^9))))} := \frac{(2 - (5 + (0 - (3 + 4))))}{(8 - (7 + (6 - 19)))} := \frac{(2 \times ((5 \times (0 + 3)) + 4))}{((8 - (7 - 6)) \times 19)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (5 - (0 - (3 \times 4))))}{((8 \times 7) + ((6 + 1) \times 9))} := \frac{(2 \times (5 - (0 - (3 + 4))))}{(8 + (76 \times (1^9)))} := \frac{(2 \times (5 - (0 - (3 - 4))))}{(8 + (7 - (6 - 19)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (5 - (0 \times 34)))}{(87 - (61 - 9))} := \frac{(2 \times (5 + (0 - (3 - 4))))}{(8 + ((7 \times 6) + (1 - 9)))} := \frac{(2 \times (50 + (3 + 4)))}{((8 + (7 + 6)) \times 19)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2^{(5-03) \times 4})}{(8 \times (7 \times (6 + (1 + 9))))} := \frac{(2^{5+0 \times 34})}{(8 \times (7 + (6 + (1^9))))} := \frac{(2 + ((5 + (0 - 3))^4))}{(8 + (7 - (6 \times (1 - 9))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (5 - (0 - (3 + 4))))}{(8 - (7 + (6 \times (1 - 9))))} := \frac{(2 + (5 - (0 - (3 - 4))))}{(8 + (7 + (6 \times (1^9))))} := \frac{(25 \times (0 + (3 \times 4)))}{((8 + 7) \times (61 + 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{(250 - 34)}{((8 + (76 \times 1)) \times 9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{28940}{36175}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((2 \times 8) + 9) \times (4 - 0))}{(3 + (61 \times (7 - 5)))} := \frac{(((2 \times 8) + 9) \times 40)}{(((3^6 - 1) + 7) \times 5)} := \frac{(((2 \times 8) - 9) \times (4 - 0))}{(36 - (1^{75}))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((2 \times 8) - 9) \times 40)}{((3 + (6 + 1)) \times (7 \times 5))} := \frac{((2 - (8 - 9)) \times (4 - 0))}{(3 \times (6 - (1^{75})))} := \frac{((2 - (8 - 9)) \times 40)}{((36 + (1 - 7)) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((36 - (1^7)) \times 5)}{((2 \times (8 \times 9)) - (4 - 0))} := \frac{((3 \times 61) + (7 - 5))}{((2 \times (8 \times 9)) + (4 - 0))} := \frac{(((3 + (6 + 1)) \times 7) - 5)}{((2 \times 8) + (9 \times (4 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + (8 + 9)) \times (4 - 0))}{((36 - 17) \times 5)} := \frac{((2 + (8 + 9)) \times 40)}{(((3 \times 61) + 7) \times 5)} := \frac{((2 + (8 - 9)) \times (4 - 0))}{(3 + (6 + ((1^7) - 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + (8 - 9)) \times 40)}{((3 + (6 + (1^7))) \times 5)} := \frac{((28 \times 9) - 40)}{((36 + 17) \times 5)} := \frac{(2 \times ((8 \times 9) + (4 - 0)))}{(2 \times ((6 - 1) \times 7)) \times 5} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((8 \times 9) + 40))}{((3 + (6 - 1)) \times (7 \times 5))} := \frac{(2 \times ((8 \times 9) - 40))}{((3 + (6 + (1 \times 7))) \times 5)} := \frac{(2 \times (8 \times (9 - (4 - 0))))}{(3 + ((6 \times 17) - 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (8 \times (9 \times (4 - 0))))}{(3 \times (6 \times ((1 + 7) \times 5)))} := \frac{(2 \times (8 \times (9 + (4 - 0))))}{((3 + ((6 + 1) \times 7)) \times 5)} := \frac{(2 \times (8 + (9 \times (4 - 0))))}{(3 + ((6 \times 17) + 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (8 + (94 - 0)))}{((3 + (6 \times (1 + 7))) \times 5)} := \frac{(2^{8-9+4+0})}{(3 + (6 + (1^{75})))} := \frac{(2 + (8 + (94 - 0)))}{((3 + (6 + 17)) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(28 \times (9 \times (4 - 0)))}{(36 \times (1 \times (7 \times 5)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{34182}{56970}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((3 \times (4 - 1))^8) \times 2)}{(5 \times (6 \times (9^7 + 0)))} := \frac{((3 \times 4) + (18^2))}{((5 - (6 - 9)) \times 70)} := \frac{((3 \times 41) + (8 - 2))}{(5 - ((6 - 9) \times 70))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3^{4-1^8}) \times 2)}{(5 + (6 + (9 + 70)))} := \frac{((3^{4 \times 1}) + (8 - 2))}{((5 \times (6 + 9)) + 70)} := \frac{((341 \times 8) + 2)}{((56 + 9) \times 70)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (4 - (1 \times 82)))}{(56 + (9 + 70))} := \frac{(3 \times ((4 - (1 - 8)) \times 2))}{(5 \times (6 + (9 + (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(3 \times (4 - (1 - (8^2))))}{(5 \times (6 - (9 - 70)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (4 - (1^{82})))}{(5 - (6 - (9 + (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(3 \times (4 - (1 - 82)))}{(5 \times (6 + (9 + 70)))} := \frac{(3 \times (4 \times ((1^8) + 2)))}{(5 - (6 + (9 - 70)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (4 \times (1 \times (8 + 2))))}{((5 \times (6 \times 9)) - 70)} := \frac{(3 \times (4 \times (1 + (8 - 2))))}{((5 + (6 - 9)) \times 70)} := \frac{(3 \times (4 \times (1^{82})))}{(5 \times (6 - (9 - (7 - 0))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (4 + (1 \times (8^2))))}{((5 \times (6 \times 9)) + 70)} &:= \frac{(3 \times (4 + (1 + (8^2))))}{(5 \times (6 + (9 \times (7 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (4 + (1 + (8 - 2))))}{((5 \times (6 - 9)) + 70)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (41 + (8^2)))}{(5 \times ((6 + 9) \times (7 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (41 + (8 - 2)))}{(5 \times ((6 \times 9) - (7 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(3^{4-1^8-2})}{((5 \times (6 + 9)) - 70)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (4 + (1 + (8 \times 2))))}{(5 \times (6 + (9 - (7 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(3 + (41 \times (8 - 2)))}{((5 \times 69) + 70)} &:= \frac{(3 + (41 + (8^2)))}{(5 \times (6^{9-7+0}))} \\
 &:= \frac{3 + 4182}{5 + 6970}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{41823}{69705}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((4 - ((1 - 8) \times 2)) \times 3)}{(6 + (9 + (70 + 5)))} &:= \frac{((4 - (1 - (8^2))) \times 3)}{((6 - (9 - 70)) \times 5)} &:= \frac{((4 - (1^{82})) \times 3)}{(6 + (9 - (7 \times (0 \times 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 - (1 - 82)) \times 3)}{((6 + (9 + 70)) \times 5)} &:= \frac{((4 \times (18 \times 2)) - 3)}{(((6 \times 9) - (7 - 0)) \times 5)} &:= \frac{((4 + (1 \times (8 - 2))) \times 3)}{(6 + (9 - (7 \times (0 - 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 + (1 + (8 \times 2))) \times 3)}{((6 - 9) \times (7 \times (0 - 5)))} &:= \frac{((4 + (1 + (8^2))) \times 3)}{((6 + (9 \times (7 - 0))) \times 5)} &:= \frac{((41 + (8 \times 2)) \times 3)}{((6 - (9 \times 7)) \times (0 - 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((41 + (8^2)) \times 3)}{((6 + 9) \times (7 \times (0 + 5)))} &:= \frac{(4 - (1 - ((8 - 2)^3)))}{(6 + (9 + (70 \times 5)))} &:= \frac{(4 - (1 - (8 - (2 - 3))))}{((6 - (9 - (7 - 0))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (1 + (8 - 23)))}{((6 + 9) \times (7 + (0 - 5)))} &:= \frac{(4 \times (((1^8) + 2)^3))}{((6^{9-7+0}) \times 5)} &:= \frac{(4 \times ((1 + 8) \times (2^3)))}{(6 \times ((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (1 + (8 + (2 \times 3))))}{(((6 + 9) \times (7 - 0)) - 5)} &:= \frac{(4 \times (18 - (2 \times 3)))}{(6 + (9 + (70 - 5)))} &:= \frac{(4 \times (18 \times (2 \times 3)))}{(6 + (9 + 705))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (1 + ((8 \times 2) + 3)))}{((6 + (9 - (7 - 0))) \times 5)} &:= \frac{(4 + (1 + ((8^2) - 3)))}{((6 + (9 + (7 - 0))) \times 5)} &:= \frac{(4 + (1 + (8 + 23)))}{(6 \times ((9 - (7 - 0)) \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (182 - 3))}{(((6 \times 9) + (7 - 0)) \times 5)} &:= \frac{(418 + (2 - 3))}{((69 + 70) \times 5)} &:= \frac{4182 + 3}{6970 + 5} \\
 &:= \frac{4182 - 3}{6970 - 5}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{67152}{83940}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((67 - 1) \times 5) + 2)}{(83 \times (9 - (4 - 0)))} &:= \frac{((6 - (7 - 15))^2)}{((8 - 3) \times (9 + 40))} &:= \frac{((6 \times (7 - (1 - 5))) + 2)}{(((8 - 3) \times 9) + 40)} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 \times (7 \times (1^5))) + 2)}{((8 + 3) \times (9 - (4 - 0)))} &:= \frac{((6 \times (7 + (1 + 5))) + 2)}{((8 \times (3 + 9)) + (4 - 0))} &:= \frac{((6^{7+1}) \times (5 - 2))}{(8 \times ((3^9) \times 40))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 + (7 + 15)) \times 2)}{(83 - (9 + (4 - 0)))} &:= \frac{((67 - (1 \times 5)) \times 2)}{(8 + (3 \times (9 + 40)))} &:= \frac{(6 - (7 - (1 + 52)))}{((8 - 3) \times (9 + (4 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 - (7 - (15^2)))}{(8 \times (39 - (4 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(6 - (7 \times (1 - (5 - 2))))}{((8 - 3) \times (9 - (4 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(6 - (7 + (1 - (5 \times 2))))}{(8 - (3 - (9 - (4 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times ((7 + 1) \times (5 \times 2)))}{(((8 \times 3) - 9) \times 40)} &:= \frac{(6 \times ((7 + 1)^{5-2}))}{(8 \times ((3 + 9) \times 40))} &:= \frac{(6 \times (7 - (1 - (5 \times 2))))}{(8 \times (3 \times (9 - (4 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (7 \times (1 \times (5 \times 2))))}{((8^3) + (9 + (4 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(6 \times (7 + (1 \times (5 + 2))))}{(8 + (3 + (94 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(6 \times (7 + (1 \times (5 - 2))))}{(8 + ((3 \times 9) + 40))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (7 + (1^{52})))}{(8 + (3 + (9 + 40)))} &:= \frac{(6 \times (7 + (15 + 2)))}{((8 - 3) \times (9 \times (4 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(6 + (7 - (1 - 52)))}{((8 + (3 - 9)) \times 40)} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 + (7 \times (1 \times (5 \times 2))))}{(((8 + 3) \times 9) - (4 - 0))} &:= \frac{(6 + (7 + (1 - (5 \times 2))))}{(((8 - 3) \times 9) - 40)} &:= \frac{(67 + (15^2))}{(8 - (3 - (9 \times 40)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(671 - (5 - 2))}{(839 - (4 - 0))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{71624}{89530} &:= \frac{(((7 \times (1+6)) + 2) \times 4)}{((8+9) \times (5 \times (3-0)))} := \frac{(((7+1) \times (6 \times 2)) - 4)}{((8 \times (9+5)) + (3-0))} := \frac{((7 - (1-6)) \times 24)}{((8 + (9-5)) \times 30)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 \times 16) - (2^4))}{((8 - (9-5)) \times 30)} := \frac{((7 + (1 \times 6)) \times 24)}{((8 \times (9 \times 5)) + 30)} := \frac{((7 + (1 + (6 \times 2))) \times 4)}{(8 + (95 - (3-0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 + (16+2)) \times 4)}{((8 \times 9) + (53-0))} := \frac{((7+1) \times (6 \times (2^4)))}{(8 \times ((9-5) \times 30))} := \frac{((7+1) \times (62+4))}{((8 + (9+5)) \times 30)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7-1) \times (6 \times 24))}{(8 \times (9 \times (5 \times (3-0))))} := \frac{((71 + (6 \times 2)) \times 4)}{((89 \times 5) - 30)} := \frac{((71+6) \times 24)}{(((8 \times 9) + 5) \times 30)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 - (1 - (6 + (2^4))))}{((8 \times (9-5)) + (3-0))} := \frac{(7 - (1 - (62-4)))}{(8 + (9 \times (5 + (3-0))))} := \frac{(7 - (1 + (6 - (2^4))))}{(8 + ((9-5) \times (3-0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 \times (1 \times (6 - (2-4))))}{(8 + (9 + (53-0)))} := \frac{(7 \times (16 \times 24))}{(8 \times ((9+5) \times 30))} := \frac{(7 + (1 - (6 \times (2-4))))}{(8 + (9 + (5 + (3-0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (1 + ((6^2) - 4)))}{(8 + ((9+5) \times (3-0)))} := \frac{(7 + (1 + ((6-2)^4))}{((8 \times (9 \times 5)) - 30)} := \frac{(7 + (1 + (6 \times (2+4))))}{(((8+9) \times 5) - 30)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (1 + (6 + (2-4))))}{(8 + (9 - (5 - (3-0))))} := \frac{(7 + (1 + 624))}{((8 \times 95) + 30)} := \frac{716 + 24}{895 + 30} \\
 &:= \frac{716 - 24}{895 - 30}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{8634}{107925} &:= \frac{(((8+6) \times 3) - 4)}{((10 - (7-92)) \times 5)} := \frac{(((8-6) \times 3) + 4)}{(1 \times (0 + ((7 + (9 \times 2)) \times 5)))} := \frac{(((8-6)^3) \times 4)}{(1 \times (0 + ((7+9) \times 25)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((8-6)^3) + 4)}{((10 \times (7+9)) - (2 \times 5))} := \frac{(((8-6)^3) - 4)}{(1 - (0 - (7^{9-2-5})))} := \frac{((8 \times (6+3)) + 4)}{(10 \times ((7 \times 9) + (2^5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((8 \times (6-3)) + 4)}{(((1 - (0-7)) \times 9) - 2) \times 5)} := \frac{((8 \times 6) + 34)}{(1 + ((0 - (7 - (9+2)))^5))} := \frac{((8-6) \times (3 \times 4))}{(10 \times (7 - (9 - (2^5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((8-6)^{3+4})}{((1 - (0 - (7 \times 9))) \times 25)} := \frac{(8 - (6 \times (3-4)))}{((10 \times (7 + (9+2))) - 5)} := \frac{(8 - (6-34))}{(10 + ((7 + (9^2)) \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 \times (6 - (3-4)))}{(10 \times (7 + (9 \times (2+5))))} := \frac{(8 \times (6 + (3 \times 4)))}{(8 \times (6 + (3-4)))} := \frac{(8 \times (6 + (3-4)))}{(8 \times (6 + (3-4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 \times ((7+9) \times 25))}{(8 + (6 \times (3+4)))} := \frac{(1 - (0-7)) \times (9 \times 25)}{(8 + ((6 \times 3) + 4))} := \frac{((1 - (0 - (7+92))) \times 5)}{(8 + ((6-3) \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(107 + (9 \times 2)) \times 5}{(8 + (6 + 34))} := \frac{(1 + (0 - (7 - (9^2)))) \times 5}{(8 + (6 \times (3-4)))} := \frac{((1 - (0 - (7 \times (9-2)))) \times 5)}{(8 + (6 + (3 \times 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 \times ((7 \times 9) + (2-5)))}{(86 - 34)} := \frac{(8 + (63 \times 4))}{(10 \times ((7 \times 9) + 2) \times 5)} := \frac{(86 - (3 \times 4))}{((10^7) \times 925)} \\
 &:= \frac{(86 - 34)}{(1 - (0 - ((7 \times 92) + 5)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{4691}{375280} &:= \frac{(((4+6) \times 9) + 1)}{(((3 \times 7) + 5) \times 280)} := \frac{((4 \times 6) - (9+1))}{(((3 \times 7) - (5+2)) \times 80)} := \frac{((4 \times 6) - (9-1))}{((3 + (7-5)) \times (2^8 + 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times 6) + (9+1))}{(((3 \times (7+5)) - 2) \times 80)} := \frac{((4 \times 6) + (9-1))}{(((3 \times 7) - 5) \times (2 \times 80))} := \frac{((4+6) \times (9+1))}{((3+7) \times (5 \times (2 \times 80)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4+6) \times (9-1))}{((3 + (75+2)) \times 80)} := \frac{((4+6)^9 \times 1)}{(((3+7)^5)^2) \times (8-0)} := \frac{(4 - (6 - (9 \times 1)))}{((3 + (7 - (5-2))) \times 80)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (6 - (9+1)))}{((3 + (75+2)) \times (8-0))} := \frac{(4 - (6 - (9-1)))}{((3 - (7 - (5 \times 2))) \times 80)} := \frac{(4 - (6-91))}{((37+52) \times 80)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 \times 91))}{(((3^7) - (5-2)) \times 80)} := \frac{(4 \times (6 + (9+1)))}{((37-5) \times (2 \times 80))} := \frac{(4 \times (6 + (9-1)))}{(((3 \times 7) - 5) \times 280)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(4 + (6 - (9 \times 1)))}{(3 + (7 \times (5 - (2 - (8 - 0)))))} := \frac{(4 + (6 - (9 - 1)))}{((3 + (7 + (5 \times 2))) \times (8 - 0))} := \frac{(4 + (6 \times (9 - 1)))}{((3 + (7 \times (5 + 2))) \times 80)} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + (6 + (9 + 1)))}{((3 + (7 + (5 \times 2))) \times 80)} := \frac{(4 + (6 + (9 - 1)))}{((3^{7-5}) \times (2 \times 80))} := \frac{(4 + (69 \times 1))}{((3 + (7 \times (5 \times 2))) \times 80)} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + (69 - 1))}{(3 \times ((7 + 5) \times (2 \times 80)))} := \frac{(46 - (9 \times 1))}{(37 \times (5 \times (2 \times (8 - 0))))} := \frac{(46 - (9 + 1))}{(((3 \times (7 - 5))^2) \times 80)} \\
 & := \frac{(46 - (9 - 1))}{(((3 \times (7 + 5)) + 2) \times 80)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{6927}{138540}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(((6 + 9)^2) - 7)}{(((13 \times 8) + 5) \times 40)} := \frac{((6 \times 9) - (2 \times 7))}{((1 + ((3 \times 8) - 5)) \times 40)} := \frac{((6 \times 9) + (2 \times 7))}{((1 + (38 - 5)) \times 40)} \\
 & := \frac{((6 \times 9) - 27)}{((1 + (3 + 8)) \times (5 + 40))} := \frac{((6 + 9) \times (2 \times 7))}{((13 + 8) \times (5 \times 40))} := \frac{((6 + 9) \times (2 + 7))}{((13 - 8) \times 540)} \\
 & := \frac{((6 - 9) \times (2 - 7))}{(((1 + 3) \times 85) - 40)} := \frac{(6 - (9 - (2 \times 7)))}{(1 \times ((3 + 8) \times (5 \times (4 - 0))))} := \frac{(6 - (9 - (2 + 7)))}{((1 - (3 - 8)) \times (5 \times (4 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 - (9 \times (2 - 7)))}{(1 \times (3 \times (85 \times (4 - 0))))} := \frac{(6 - (9 + (2 - 7)))}{(1 \times (3 - (8 - (5 + 40))))} := \frac{(6 - (9 - 27))}{(1 \times (3 \times (8 \times (5 \times (4 - 0)))))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 \times ((9 \times 2) - 7))}{(1 \times ((38 - 5) \times 40))} := \frac{(6 \times (9 + (2 \times 7)))}{(138 \times (5 \times (4 - 0)))} := \frac{(6 \times (9 + 27))}{((1^3) \times (8 \times 540))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 \times (92 - 7))}{(1 \times (3 \times (85 \times 40)))} := \frac{(6 + ((9 \times 2) + 7))}{(1 \times (3 - (8 - (5^4 + 0))))} := \frac{(6 + ((9 \times 2) - 7))}{((1^3) \times (85 \times (4 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 + ((9^2) - 7))}{((1 + (3 \times (8 + 5))) \times 40)} := \frac{(6 + (9 - (2 \times 7)))}{(1 \times (3 + (8 + (5 + (4 - 0)))))} := \frac{(6 + (9 - (2 - 7)))}{((1 + (3 \times (8 - 5))) \times 40)} \\
 & := \frac{(6 + (9 + (2 - 7)))}{(((1^3)^8) \times (5 \times 40))} := \frac{(69 - (2 + 7))}{((1 - (3 - 8)) \times (5 \times 40))} := \frac{(69 - (2 - 7))}{(((1 + 3) \times 8) + 5) \times 40)} \\
 & := \frac{(69 + (2 + 7))}{(1 \times (3 \times ((8 + 5) \times 40)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{7596}{182304}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(((7 + 5) \times 9) - 6)}{(1 \times (8 \times (2 + 304)))} := \frac{(((7 - 5) \times 9) + 6)}{(18 \times ((2^3 + 0) \times 4))} := \frac{(((7 - 5) \times 9) - 6)}{(1 \times (8 \times (2 + (30 + 4))))} \\
 & := \frac{(((7 - 5)^9) \times 6)}{(18 \times ((2^3 + 0)^4))} := \frac{((7 \times 5) - (9 - 6))}{(1 \times ((8^2) \times (3 \times (0 + 4))))} := \frac{((7 \times 5) + (9 + 6))}{(1 \times ((8 + 2) \times (30 \times 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{((7 \times 5) + (9 - 6))}{(((1^8) + 2) \times 304)} := \frac{((7 + (5 - 9)) \times 6)}{(18 \times (2 \times (3 \times (0 + 4))))} := \frac{((7 + 5) \times (9 + 6))}{(18 \times (2 \times (30 \times 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{((7 + 5) \times (9 - 6))}{(1 \times (((8 - 2)^3 + 0) \times 4))} := \frac{((7 + 5)^{9-6})}{(18 \times 2304)} := \frac{((7 - 5) \times (9 + 6))}{(1 \times ((8 - 2) \times (30 \times 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{((7 - 5) \times (9 - 6))}{(1 \times ((8 - (2 - 30)) \times 4))} := \frac{((7 - 5)^{9-6})}{(1 \times (8 \times (2 \times (3 \times (0 + 4)))))} := \frac{(7 - (5 - (9 - 6)))}{(1 \times (8 - ((2 - 30) \times 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{(7 \times (5 - (9 - 6)))}{((1 - (82 + 3)) \times (0 - 4))} := \frac{(7^{5-9+6})}{(((18^2) - 30) \times 4)} := \frac{(7 + ((5 + 9) \times 6))}{(182 \times (3 \times (0 + 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{(7 + (5 - (9 - 6)))}{(1 \times (8 \times (23 - (0 - 4))))} := \frac{(7 + (5 + (9 + 6)))}{(18 \times (2 + (30 + 4)))} := \frac{(7 + (5 + (9 - 6)))}{(18 \times ((2 + (3 - 0)) \times 4))} \\
 & := \frac{(75 - (9 \times 6))}{(18 \times (2 + (30 - 4)))} := \frac{(75 + (9 + 6))}{((1 + 8) \times (2 \times (30 \times 4)))} := \frac{(75 + (9 - 6))}{(1 \times (8 \times (230 + 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{(75 + 96)}{(1 \times (8 + ((2^3 + 0)^4))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{7692}{153840} &:= \frac{(((7-6)^9)+2)}{(1 \times (5 \times (3 \times (8-(4-0)))))} := \frac{((7 \times (6 \times 9))+2)}{(1 \times (5 \times (38 \times 40)))} := \frac{((7 \times 6) + (9 \times 2))}{((1 + (5 + (3 \times 8))) \times 40)} \\ &:= \frac{((7 + (6 \times 9)) \times 2)}{(1 \times ((53+8) \times 40))} := \frac{((7 + (6-9))^2)}{(1 \times (5 \times ((3 \times 8) + 40)))} := \frac{((7+6) \times (9 \times 2))}{(1 \times (((5^3) - 8) \times 40))} \\ &:= \frac{((7-6) \times (9 \times 2))}{(((1^{53}) + 8) \times 40)} := \frac{((7-6) \times (9+2))}{(1 \times (5 \times ((3+8) \times (4-0))))} := \frac{((7-6) \times (9-2))}{((7-6) \times (9-2))} \\ &:= \frac{((7-6) \times 92)}{((1 + (53-8)) \times 40)} := \frac{(7 - ((6-9) \times 2))}{(1 \times (((5-3)^8) + (4-0)))} := \frac{(7 - (6 - (9 \times 2)))}{(1 - (5 - (384 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 - (6 - (9+2)))}{(((1^5) - (3-8)) \times 40)} := \frac{(7 - (6 - (9-2)))}{(1 \times ((5 \times (3 \times 8)) + 40))} := \frac{(7 \times (6 \times (9 \times 2)))}{(7 \times (6 \times (9 \times 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 \times (6 + (9 \times 2)))}{(((1^5) + 3) \times 840)} := \frac{(7 + ((6 \times 9) + 2))}{(1 \times (5 \times (3 \times (84 - 0))))} := \frac{(7 + ((6-9) \times 2))}{((15+3) \times 840)} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + (6 - (9+2)))}{(1 \times (5 + (3 - (8-40))))} := \frac{(7 + (6 - (9-2)))}{(1 \times (5 \times (3 \times (84 - 0))))} := \frac{(7 + (6 + (9+2)))}{(1 \times (5 + (3 + (8 + (4-0)))))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + (6 + (9-2)))}{(1 \times ((5 - (3-8)) \times 40))} := \frac{(7 + (69+2))}{((1 + (5 + (3 \times 8))) \times (4-0))} := \frac{(7 + (69-2))}{(1 \times (5 \times (3 \times (8 \times (4-0)))))} \\ &:= \frac{(76 - (9 \times 2))}{(1 \times ((5 + (3 \times 8)) \times 40))} := \frac{(7 + (69+2))}{((15 + (3 \times 8)) \times 40)} := \frac{(7 + (69-2))}{(((15 \times 3) - 8) \times 40)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{8694}{217350} &:= \frac{(((8-6) \times 9) + 4)}{((2 - (1 - (7+3))) \times 50)} := \frac{(((8-6) \times 9) - 4)}{(2 + (1 \times ((7^3) + (5-0))))} := \frac{(((8-6)^9) \times 4)}{(2 \times (((1+7)^3) \times 50))} \\ &:= \frac{((8 - (6-9)) \times 4)}{(2 \times ((1 + (7+3)) \times 50))} := \frac{((8 \times (6 \times 9)) - 4)}{((217 - 3) \times 50)} := \frac{((8 \times 6) - (9 \times 4))}{((8 \times 6) - (9 \times 4))} \\ &:= \frac{((8 \times 6) - (9+4))}{((2 + 173) \times (5-0))} := \frac{((8 \times 6) + (9 \times 4))}{(2 \times (1 \times (7 \times (3 \times 50))))} := \frac{((8-6) \times (9^4))}{(((2+1)^7) \times (3 \times 50))} \\ &:= \frac{((8-6) \times (9+4))}{((2 + (1 + (7+3))) \times 50)} := \frac{((8-6) \times (9-4))}{((2 - (1 - (7-3))) \times 50)} := \frac{((8-6) \times 94)}{((8-6) \times 94)} \\ &:= \frac{((8-6)^{9-4})}{((2 \times (1 \times (7-3))) \times 50)} := \frac{(8 - ((6-9) \times 4))}{(2 \times (1 \times (7 + (3^5 + 0))))} := \frac{(8 - (6 - (9+4)))}{((2 + (1 \times 73)) \times (5-0))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 - (6 - (9-4)))}{((2^{1 \times 7}) - (3-50))} := \frac{(8 - (6-94))}{(2 \times ((1+7) \times (3 \times 50)))} := \frac{(8 \times (6 + (9+4)))}{(8 \times (6 + (9+4)))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 \times (6 + (9-4)))}{(2 \times ((1 + (7 \times 3)) \times 50))} := \frac{(8^{6-9+4})}{(2 \times ((17+3) \times (5-0)))} := \frac{(8 + (6 - (9+4)))}{(2 + (1 + (7 + (3 \times (5-0)))))} \\ &:= \frac{(8 + (6 - (9-4)))}{(2 + (173 + 50))} := \frac{(8 + (6 \times (9 \times 4)))}{(2 \times ((1+7) \times 350))} := \frac{(8 + (6 \times (9-4)))}{(((2 + (1+7))^3) - 50)} \\ &:= \frac{(8 + (6 + (9 \times 4)))}{(21 + (7-3)) \times 50} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{9648}{135072} &:= \frac{(((9+6) \times 4) + 8)}{(((1+3)^5 + 0) - 72)} := \frac{(((9-6) \times 4) + 8)}{((1+3) \times (5 \times (0 + (7 \times 2))))} := \frac{(((9-6) \times 4) - 8)}{(1 \times ((35 + (0-7)) \times 2))} \\ &:= \frac{((9 - (6-4)) \times 8)}{((1 + (3 \times (5-0))) \times (7^2))} := \frac{((9 \times (6 \times 4)) + 8)}{(1 \times (((3 + (5-0)) \times 7^2))} := \frac{((9 \times (6-4)) + 8)}{(1 + (3 - (5 \times (0-72))))} \\ &:= \frac{((9 \times (6-4)) - 8)}{((13 + (50+7)) \times 2)} := \frac{((9 \times 6) - (4 \times 8))}{((1+3) \times (5 - (0-72)))} := \frac{((9 \times 6) + (4-8))}{((1^3) \times (50 \times (7 \times 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{((9 \times 6) - 48)}{(1 - (3 - ((50-7) \times 2)))} := \frac{((9^{6-4}) - 8)}{((1 + (3 + 507)) \times 2)} := \frac{((9+6) \times (4+8))}{(1 \times (35 \times (0+72)))} \\ &:= \frac{((9-6) \times (4+8))}{((1 + (35-0)) \times (7 \times 2))} := \frac{(9 - (6 - (4 \times 8)))}{(1 \times (35 \times (0 + (7 \times 2))))} := \frac{(9 - (6 - (4+8)))}{(1 \times (3 \times (5 \times (0 + (7 \times 2)))))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(9 - (6 + (4 - 8)))}{(1 \times ((3 - 5) \times (0 - (7^2))))} := \frac{(9 - (6 - 48))}{(1 \times ((350 + 7) \times 2))} := \frac{(9 \times (6 + (4 - 8)))}{(1 \times ((3^5 + 0) + (7 + 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 + ((6 - 4) \times 8))}{(1 - (3 - ((50 \times 7) + 2)))} := \frac{(9 + (6 - (4 + 8)))}{(1 - (3 + (5 + (0 - (7^2)))))} := \frac{(9 + (6 - (4 - 8)))}{(1 + ((3 + 50) \times (7 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 + (6 + (4 - 8)))}{((13 \times (5 - (0 - 7))) - 2)} := \frac{(9 + (6 + 48))}{((13 + 50) \times (7 \times 2))} := \frac{(9 + (64 - 8))}{(13 \times (5 \times (0 + (7 \times 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(96 - 48)}{((1 - (3 - 50)) \times (7 \times 2))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{7923}{158460}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((7 \times 9) - 2) \times 3)}{((1 + (5 \times (8 + 4))) \times 60)} := \frac{(((7 + 9) \times 2) - 3)}{(1 \times (58 \times (4 + (6 - 0))))} := \frac{(((7 + 9)^2) \times 3)}{(((1 - (5 - 8))^4) \times 60)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 \times 9) - (2 \times 3))}{((15 + (8 - 4)) \times 60)} := \frac{((7 \times 9) + (2 \times 3))}{(15 \times ((8 \times 4) + 60))} := \frac{((7 \times 9) + (2 - 3))}{(1 \times (5 \times (8 + (4 \times 60))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 + (9 + 2)) \times 3)}{((1 + (5 + (8 + 4))) \times 60)} := \frac{((7 + 9) \times (2^3))}{(1 \times (5 \times (8 \times (4 + 60))))} := \frac{((7 + 92) \times 3)}{((15 + 84) \times 60)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 - 9) \times (2 - 3))}{((1 - (5 - 8)) \times (4 + (6 - 0)))} := \frac{((79 \times 2) + 3)}{((15 - 8) \times 460)} := \frac{(7 - (9 - (2 \times 3)))}{(1 \times ((5 \times (8 - 4)) + 60))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 - (9 - (2^3)))}{(1 \times (5 \times (84 - 60)))} := \frac{(7 - (9 - (2 + 3)))}{(1 - (5 - (8 - (4 - 60))))} := \frac{(7 - (9 \times (2 - 3)))}{(1 \times (5 \times (8 - (4 - 60))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 - (9 - 23))}{((15 \times (8 \times 4)) - 60)} := \frac{(7 \times (9 \times (2 \times 3)))}{(15 \times (84 \times (6 - 0)))} := \frac{7^{9-2^3}}{1 - 5 + 84 + 60} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (9 - (2^3)))}{(1 \times (5 \times (8 + (4 \times (6 - 0)))))} := \frac{(7 + (9 - (2 + 3)))}{(1 \times ((5 \times (8 \times 4)) + 60))} := \frac{(7 + (9 \times (2^3)))}{(158 \times (4 + (6 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (9 + (2^3)))}{((1 - (5 - 84)) \times (6 - 0))} := \frac{(7 + (9 + (2 - 3)))}{(((1^5) + (8 - 4)) \times 60)} := \frac{(7 + (9 + 23))}{((1 - ((5 - 8) \times 4)) \times 60)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (92 - 3))}{((1^5) \times (8 \times (4 \times 60)))} := \frac{(79 + (2 + 3))}{((1 - (5 - (8 \times 4))) \times 60)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{8235}{197640}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((8 \times 2) + 3) \times 5)}{(1 \times (((9 \times 7) - 6) \times 40))} := \frac{(((8^2) \times 3) + 5)}{(197 \times (6 \times (4 - 0)))} := \frac{(((8 - 2) \times 3) + 5)}{((19 - 7) \times (6 + 40))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((8 - 2)^3) - 5)}{((1 - 9) \times (7 - 640))} := \frac{((8 - (2 \times 3)) \times 5)}{((1^9) \times (6 \times 40))} := \frac{((8 - (2 + 3)) \times 5)}{(1 \times (9 \times ((7 - 6) \times 40)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((8 \times 2) - (3 \times 5))}{(1 + (9 + (7 \times (6 - (4 - 0)))))} := \frac{((8 + (2 \times 3)) \times 5)}{((1^9) \times (7 \times (6 \times 40)))} := \frac{((8 + 2)^{3+5})}{(((1 + 9)^7) \times (6 \times 40))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 - ((2 \times 3) - 5))}{((1^9) \times (7 \times (6 \times (4 - 0))))} := \frac{(8 - ((2^3) - 5))}{((19 - 7) \times (6 + (4 - 0)))} := \frac{(8 - ((2 - 3) \times 5))}{((1 - 9) \times (7 - (6 + 40)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 - (2 - (3 - 5)))}{(1 + (97 - (6 - (4 - 0))))} := \frac{(8 - (2 + (3 - 5)))}{((1 + (9 - 7)) \times (64 - 0))} := \frac{(8 \times ((2^3) \times 5))}{((19 - 7) \times 640)} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 \times (2 - (3 - 5)))}{((19 - 7) \times (64 - 0))} := \frac{(8 \times (2 + (3 \times 5)))}{((1 - 97) \times (6 - 40))} := \frac{(8 \times (2 + (3 + 5)))}{((1 + (9 - 7)) \times 640)} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 + ((2 \times 3) + 5))}{((1 - 9) \times (7 - (64 - 0)))} := \frac{(8 + ((2 \times 3) - 5))}{((1 - 9) \times (7 + (6 - 40)))} := \frac{(8 + ((2 - 3) \times 5))}{(1 - (9 - (76 + (4 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 + (2 - (3 + 5)))}{(1 \times (9 - (7 - (6 + 40))))} := \frac{(8 + (2 - (3 - 5)))}{((19 - 7) \times (6 \times (4 - 0)))} := \frac{(8 + (23 - 5))}{((19 + 7) \times (6 \times (4 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(82 - (3 - 5))}{(1976 + 40)} := \frac{(82 + (3 \times 5))}{(1 \times (97 \times (6 \times (4 - 0))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{8746}{109325} &:= \frac{(((8+7) \times 4) - 6)}{(1 \times (0 + (9 \times (3 \times 25))))} &:= \frac{(((8-7)^4) \times 6)}{((1 - (0 - (9 + (3 + 2)))) \times 5)} &:= \frac{((8 \times (7 \times 4)) + 6)}{((10 \times (9 \times 32)) - 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((8 \times (7 \times 4)) - 6)}{(109 \times ((3 + 2) \times 5))} &:= \frac{((8 \times (7 + 4)) - 6)}{(1 - (0 - ((9 - (3 + 2))^5)))} &:= \frac{((8 \times (7 - 4)) - 6)}{(1 \times (0 + (9 \times ((3 + 2) \times 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((8 \times 7) - (4 \times 6))}{(10 \times ((9 - (3 - 2)) \times 5))} &:= \frac{((8 \times 7) - (4 - 6))}{((1 - (0 - ((9 + 3)^2))) \times 5)} &:= \frac{((8 \times 7) + (4 \times 6))}{(10^{9-3+2-5})} \\
 &:= \frac{((8 + (7 \times 4)) \times 6)}{(10 \times (9 \times (3 \times (2 \times 5))))} &:= \frac{((8 + (7 + 4)) \times 6)}{((10 + 9) \times (3 \times 25))} &:= \frac{((8 + 7) \times (4 \times 6))}{(((1 + 09) \times 3)^2) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((8 - 7) \times (4 \times 6))}{(1 \times (0 + ((9 + 3) \times 25)))} &:= \frac{((8 - 7) \times (4 + 6))}{(1 \times (0 + (93 + (2^5))))} &:= \frac{((8 - 7) \times 46)}{((109 + (3 \times 2)) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 - (7 \times (4 - 6)))}{((1 - (0 - (9 \times (3 \times 2)))) \times 5)} &:= \frac{(8 \times ((7 - 4) \times 6))}{(10 \times (((9 - 3)^2) \times 5))} &:= \frac{(8 \times ((7 - 4)^6))}{(10 \times ((9^3) \times (2 \times 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 \times (7 - (4 - 6)))}{(10 \times (9 \times (3 + (2 + 5))))} &:= \frac{(8 \times (7 \times (4 + 6)))}{(((1 + 09)^3) \times (2 + 5))} &:= \frac{(8 \times (7 + (4 - 6)))}{(10 \times ((9 + (3 - 2)) \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 + ((7 \times 4) + 6))}{((10 + (93 + 2)) \times 5)} &:= \frac{(8 + ((7 + 4) \times 6))}{((10 + (9 \times 3)) \times 25)} &:= \frac{(8 + ((7 - 4) \times 6))}{((1 - (0 - (9 + 3))) \times 25)} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 + (7 \times (4 + 6)))}{(((1 + 09)^3) - 25)} &:= \frac{(8 + (74 + 6))}{(1093 + (2 + 5))} &
 \end{aligned}$$

3.25 26 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15384}{76920} &:= \frac{(((1 + (5 \times 3)) \times 8) + 4)}{(((7 \times 6) - 9) \times 20)} &:= \frac{((1^5) + (3 + 84))}{((7 + (6 + 9)) \times 20)} &:= \frac{((1 + (5^3)) \times (8 + 4))}{(7 \times (6 \times (9 \times 20)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (53 - 8)) \times 4)}{((7 - 6) \times 920)} &:= \frac{((1 + 5) \times (38 - 4))}{(((7 \times 6) + 9) \times 20)} &:= \frac{(1 - (5 + ((3 - 8) \times 4)))}{((7 + (6 - 9)) \times 20)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (5 + (3 - (8 \times 4))))}{((7 \times (6 + 9)) + 20)} &:= \frac{(1 \times (((5^3) - 8) \times 4))}{((7 + 6) \times (9 \times 20))} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((53 \times 8) - 4))}{(7 \times ((6 + 9) \times 20))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((53 + 8) \times 4))}{((7 + (6 \times 9)) \times 20)} &:= \frac{(1 \times (5 - (3 - (8 \times 4))))}{((76 + 9) \times (2 - 0))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (5 - (3 - (8 - 4))))}{(7 - (6 - (9 + 20)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (5 + ((3 + 8) \times 4))}{(7 \times (6 + (9 + 20)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (5 + (3 - (8 - 4))))}{(7 + (6 + (9 - (2 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (5 + (3 \times (8 - 4))))}{((7 \times (6 + 9)) - 20)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (5 + (3 + (8 \times 4))))}{((7 - (6 - 9)) \times 20)} &:= \frac{(1 \times (5 + (3 + (8 + 4))))}{((7 - (6 - 9))^2 + 0)} &:= \frac{(1 \times (5 + (3 + (8 - 4))))}{((7 \times 6) + (9 \times (2 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (((5 \times 3) - 8) \times 4))}{(7 + (69 \times (2 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 + ((5 + 3) \times (8 + 4)))}{((7 \times 69) + (2 - 0))} &:= \frac{(1 + (5 - (3 - (8 - 4))))}{((7 \times 6) - (9 - (2 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (5 \times (3 + (8 + 4))))}{((7 \times (6 \times 9)) + (2 - 0))} &:= \frac{(1 + (5 \times (3 + (8 - 4))))}{(1 + (5 \times (3 + (8 - 4))))} &:= \frac{(1 + (5 + (3 \times (8 + 4))))}{(1 + (5 + (3 \times (8 + 4))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (5 + (3 + (8 + 4))))}{((7 \times (6 \times 9)) + (2 - 0))} &:= \frac{(1 + (5 + (3 + (8 - 4))))}{((7 - 6) \times (9 \times 20))} &:= \frac{(1 + (5 + (3 + (8 - 4))))}{(7 \times ((6 + 9) \times (2 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (5 + (3 + (8 + 4))))}{(7 + (6 + (92 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (5 + (3 + (8 - 4))))}{(76 + (9 - 20))} &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17028}{93654} &:= \frac{(((1 + 70) \times 2) - 8)}{(9 + ((3^6) - (5 - 4)))} &:= \frac{(((1 - 7) \times (0 - 2)) + 8)}{((9^3) + (6 - (5^4)))} &:= \frac{((1 - (7 \times (0 - 2))) \times 8)}{(9 - (3 - 654))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1^7 + 0) \times 28)}{(93 + (65 - 4))} &:= \frac{((1 + (7 + (0 - 2))) \times 8)}{((9 - 3) \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))} &:= \frac{((1 + (70 - 2)) \times 8)}{(((9^3) + (6 \times 5)) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 - 7) \times (0 - (2 \times 8)))}{((9 + 3) \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))} &:= \frac{(1 - (7 + (0 - (2 + 8))))}{((9 \times (3 - (6 - 5))) + 4)} &:= \frac{(1 - (7 + (0 - 28)))}{((9 \times ((3 \times 6) - 5)) + 4)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((7 - (0 - 2)) \times 8))}{((9 + (3 \times (6 \times 5))) \times 4)} := \frac{(1 \times ((7 \times (0 + 2)) - 8))}{(93 - (6 + 54))} := \frac{(1 \times ((70 \times 2) + 8))}{((9 \times (3 \times (6 \times 5))) + 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((70 \times 2) - 8))}{((9^3) + (6 - (5 + 4)))} := \frac{(1 \times (7 \times ((0 \times 2) + 8)))}{((9 + (3 + 65)) \times 4)} := \frac{(1 \times (7 \times (0 + (2 \times 8))))}{((9 \times (3 + 65)) + 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (70 - (2 \times 8)))}{(((9 \times 3) + 6) \times (5 + 4))} := \frac{(1 \times (70 - (2 + 8)))}{(9 - (3 - (6 \times 54)))} := \frac{(1 + (7 - ((0 \times 2) - 8)))}{((9 + ((3 \times 6) - 5)) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{((9 + (3 + (6 \times (5 \times 4))))}{(1 + (7 - (0 - (2 \times 8))))} := \frac{(1 + (7 - (0 - (2 + 8))))}{(1 + (7 - (0 - (2 + 8))))} := \frac{(1 + (7 - (0 - (2 - 8))))}{(1 + (7 - (0 - (2 - 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 + (3 + (6 \times (5 \times 4))))}{(1 + (7 - (0 \times 28)))} := \frac{(9 + (36 + 54))}{(1 + (7 + (0 - (2 - 8))))} := \frac{(9 - (3 - (6 - (5 - 4))))}{(17 \times (0 + (2 \times 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 + (3 - (6 - 5))) \times 4}{(17 \times (0 + (2 + 8)))} := \frac{((9^{3-6+5}) - 4)}{(170 + 2 + 8)} := \frac{((9 + 365) \times 4)}{(936 - (5 - 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{170 + 2 + 8}{936 + 54}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{21843}{50967}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (18 \times 4)) - 3)}{((50 - (9 - 6)) \times 7)} := \frac{((2 \times (1 \times (8 - 4))) \times 3)}{((5 \times (0 + 9)) + 67)} := \frac{((2 + (1^{84}))^3)}{(5 + (0 - (9 - 67)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + (1^8))^{4+3})}{(5096 + 7)} := \frac{((2 + (1 + (8 \times 4))) \times 3)}{((50 - (9 + 6)) \times 7)} := \frac{((2 + (1 + (8 + 4))) \times 3)}{(5 \times (0 + ((9 - 6) \times 7)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + 1) \times (8 + 43))}{(((5 \times (0 + 9)) + 6) \times 7)} := \frac{((21 + (8 \times 4)) \times 3)}{((50 + (9 - 6)) \times 7)} := \frac{(2 - (((1 - 8) \times 4) - 3))}{(((5 - (0 - 9)) \times 6) - 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - ((1 - 8) \times (4^3)))}{(50 \times ((9 - 6) \times 7))} := \frac{(2 - ((1 - 8) \times 43))}{((5 - (0 - 96)) \times 7)} := \frac{(2 - (1 \times (8 - (4 \times 3))))}{(5 + (0 - (9 \times (6 - 7))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((1 + (8 + 4)) \times 3))}{((5 - (0 - 9)) \times (6 + 7))} := \frac{(2 \times (1 \times ((8 - 4) \times 3)))}{(5 - (0 - (9 + (6 \times 7))))} := \frac{(2 \times (1 + ((8 \times 4) - 3)))}{((5 - (0 - (9 + 6))) \times 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (1 + (8 \times (4 - 3))))}{((5 \times (0 \times 9)) + (6 \times 7))} := \frac{(2 \times (18 \times (4 + 3)))}{((5 - (0 - 9)) \times (6 \times 7))} := \frac{2 + 1^{843}}{((5 \times (0 \times 96)) + 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (1 + ((8 + 4) \times 3)))}{(((5 - (0 - 9)) \times 6) + 7)} := \frac{(2 + (1 + ((8 - 4) \times 3)))}{(2 + (1 + (8 + (4 - 3))))} := \frac{(50 - (9 + (6 + 7)))}{(21 + (8 \times (4 \times 3)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (1 + (8 + 43)))}{(50 + (9 + 67))} := \frac{(2 + (1 + (84 + 3)))}{(5 \times ((0 \times 9) + (6 \times 7)))} := \frac{(50 - (9 + (6 + 7)))}{((5 \times (0 + 9)) - 6) \times 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{(218 + (4 + 3))}{(5 \times (0 + ((9 + 6) \times 7)))} := \frac{(2184 - 3)}{(5096 - 7)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{63124}{78905}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((6 \times (3 \times 1))^2) + 4)}{((7 - 89) \times (0 - 5))} := \frac{(((6 \times (3 \times 1)) + 2) \times 4)}{(7 + (8 + (90 - 5)))} := \frac{(((6 \times (3 - 1)) + 2) \times 4)}{((7 \times 8) + (9 + 05))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((6 \times 31) - 2) \times 4)}{(7 + (8 + 905))} := \frac{(((6 + (3 + 1))^2) + 4)}{(((7 + 8) \times (9 - 0)) - 5)} := \frac{(((6 + 3) \times 12) + 4)}{(((7 + 8) \times (9 - 0)) + 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 \times 31) - (2 - 4))}{(((7 \times 8) - (9 - 0)) \times 5)} := \frac{((6^{3-1^2}) + 4)}{((7 - (8 + 9)) \times (0 - 5))} := \frac{((6^{3-1}) + (2^4))}{((7 \times 8) + (9 - (0 \times 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6^3) \times (1 + 24))}{((7 + 8) \times (90 \times 5))} := \frac{((6 + ((3 + 1)^2)) \times 4)}{(7 + (8 + (90 + 5)))} := \frac{((63 + (1 \times 2)) \times 4)}{((7 - (8 \times 9)) \times (0 - 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((63 - 1) \times (2 + 4))}{(7 + (8 + (90 \times 5)))} := \frac{(6 - (3 - (1 + 24)))}{(7 \times ((8 - 9) \times (0 - 5)))} := \frac{(6 \times ((3 - (1^2))^4))}{((7 + (8 + (9 - 0))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times ((3 - 1)^{2+4}))}{((7 + (89 - 0)) \times 5)} := \frac{(6 \times ((31 \times 2) - 4))}{((78 + (9 - 0)) \times 5)} := \frac{(6 \times (3 - (1 - (2^4))))}{((7 + 8) \times (9 - (0 \times 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (3 - (1 - (2 + 4))))}{(7 + (8 - (9 \times (0 - 5))))} := \frac{(6 \times (3 + (1 - (2 - 4))))}{((7 - 8) \times (9 \times (0 - 5)))} := \frac{(6 \times (3 + (1 + 24)))}{((7 + 8) \times (9 + 05))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(6 + (3 - (1 - (2^4))))}{((7 + (8 - (9 - 0))) \times 5)} := \frac{(6 + (3 - (1 - 24)))}{((7 - (8 - (9 - 0))) \times 5)} := \frac{(6 + (3 + (1 - (2 - 4))))}{(7 + (8 - (9 \times (0 \times 5))))} \\ &:= \frac{6312 + 4}{7890 + 5} := \frac{6312 - 4}{7890 - 5} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{1647}{395280} &:= \frac{((1^{64}) \times 7)}{((3 + 9) \times (5 \times (28 - 0)))} := \frac{((1^{64}) + 7)}{(3 \times ((9 - 5) \times (2 \times 80)))} := \frac{((1^6) \times (4 \times 7))}{(3 \times ((9 + 5) \times (2 \times 80)))} \\ &:= \frac{((1^6) \times 47)}{(3 \times (((9 \times 5) + 2) \times 80))} := \frac{((1^6) + (4 + 7))}{(3 \times ((9 + (5 - 2)) \times 80))} := \frac{((1^6) + 47)}{(((3 \times (9 - 5))^2) \times 80)} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + (6 - 4))^7)}{((3^{(9-5) \times 2}) \times 80)} := \frac{((1 + 6) \times (4 \times 7))}{(3 \times (((9 + 5)^2) \times 80))} := \frac{(1 - (6 - (4 + 7)))}{(3 \times ((9 - (5 - 2)) \times 80))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (6 \times (4 - 7)))}{(3 \times ((9 + (5 \times 2)) \times 80))} := \frac{(1 \times ((6 \times 4) + 7))}{((3 + (9 \times (5 \times 2))) \times 80)} := \frac{(1 \times ((6 + 4) \times 7))}{((3 + 9) \times (5 \times 280))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times ((6 - 4) \times 7))}{(3 \times ((9 - 5) \times 280))} := \frac{(1 \times (6 - (4 - 7)))}{(3 \times (9 \times (5 \times (2 \times (8 - 0)))))} := \frac{(1 \times (6 + (4 \times 7)))}{(3 \times ((9 + (5^2)) \times 80))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (6 + (4 - 7)))}{((3 + (9 - (5 - 2))) \times 80)} := \frac{(1^{647})}{((3 + (9 \times (5 - 2))) \times (8 - 0))} := \frac{(1 + ((6 \times 4) + 7))}{((3 + (95 - 2)) \times 80)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (6 - (4 - 7)))}{((3 + (9 \times (5 - 2))) \times 80)} := \frac{(1 + (6 + (4 - 7)))}{((3 + 9) \times (5 \times (2 \times (8 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 + (6 + 47))}{((3^{9-5}) \times (2 \times 80))} \\ &:= \frac{(16 - (4 + 7))}{((3 + (9 + (5 - 2))) \times 80)} := \frac{(16 + (4 + 7))}{(3 \times (9 \times ((5 - 2) \times 80)))} := \frac{(16 + (4 - 7))}{(39 \times (5 \times (2 \times (8 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(16 + 47)}{(3 \times (9 \times ((5 + 2) \times 80)))} := \frac{(164 - 7)}{(3 + (9 \times 52)) \times 80} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{2937}{146850} &:= \frac{((2 \times (9 + 3)) - 7)}{((1 - ((4 - 6) \times 8)) \times 50)} := \frac{((2 \times (9 - 3)) + 7)}{((1 + (4 + (6 + 8))) \times 50)} := \frac{((2 \times (9 - 3)) - 7)}{(((1 + (4 \times 6)) \times 8) + 50)} \\ &:= \frac{((2 \times 9) + 37)}{((1 + (46 + 8)) \times 50)} := \frac{((2 \times 93) + 7)}{((1 + (4 \times (6 \times 8))) \times 50)} := \frac{((2^{9-3}) - 7)}{((1 + (4 \times (6 + 8))) \times 50)} \\ &:= \frac{((2 + (9 - 3)) \times 7)}{(1 \times (4 \times ((6 + 8) \times 50)))} := \frac{((2 - 9) \times (3 - 7))}{((14 + (6 + 8)) \times 50)} := \frac{((29 \times 3) - 7)}{(1 \times ((4 + 6) \times (8 \times 50)))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (9 - (3 \times 7)))}{((1^4) \times ((6 + 8) \times 50))} := \frac{(2 - (9 - (3 + 7)))}{((1 + (4 + (6 - 8))) \times 50)} := \frac{(2 - (9 \times (3 - 7)))}{(1 \times ((46 - 8) \times 50))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times ((9 \times 3) + 7))}{((1^4) \times (68 \times 50))} := \frac{(2 \times (9 + 37))}{(((14 \times 6) + 8) \times 50)} := \frac{(2 \times (93 + 7))}{((1 + (4 \times 6)) \times (8 \times 50))} \\ &:= \frac{(2^{9+3-7})}{(1 \times (((4 \times 6) + 8) \times 50))} := \frac{(2 + ((9 \times 3) - 7))}{((((1 + 4) \times 6) - 8) \times 50)} := \frac{(2 + (9 - (3 + 7)))}{(1 \times (4 + (6 + (8 \times (5 - 0)))))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (9 - (3 - 7)))}{(((1^4) + (6 + 8)) \times 50)} := \frac{(2 + (9 + (3 - 7)))}{((1 + (4 - (6 - 8))) \times 50)} := \frac{(2 + (9 + 37))}{((1^4) \times (6 \times (8 \times 50)))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (93 + 7))}{((1^4) \times (6 \times 850))} := \frac{(2 + (93 - 7))}{((1 + (4 + 6)) \times (8 \times 50))} := \frac{(29 - (3 \times 7))}{(1 \times ((4 + 6) \times (8 \times (5 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(29 - (3 - 7))}{((1 + ((4 \times 6) + 8)) \times 50)} := \frac{(29 + (3 + 7))}{((1 + (46 - 8)) \times 50)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{5791}{463280} &:= \frac{((5 \times 7) - (9 \times 1))}{(4 \times ((63 + 2) \times (8 - 0)))} := \frac{((5 \times 7) - (9 + 1))}{(((4 \times 63) - 2) \times (8 - 0))} := \frac{((5 \times 7) + (9 \times 1))}{(4 \times ((6 + (3 + 2)) \times 80))} \\ &:= \frac{((5 \times 7) + (9 + 1))}{((46 - (3 - 2)) \times 80)} := \frac{((5 \times 7) + 91)}{(4 \times ((6 + 3) \times 280))} := \frac{((5 + 7) \times (9 \times 1))}{(4 \times ((6^3) \times (2 + (8 - 0))))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((5+7) \times (9+1))}{(4 \times (6 \times ((3+2) \times 80)))} := \frac{((5+7) \times (9-1))}{((4+6) \times (3 \times (2^8+0)))} := \frac{(5-(7-(9 \times 1)))}{((4-(6-(3^2))) \times 80)} \\
 &:= \frac{(5-(7-(9+1)))}{((4^{6-3}) \times (2+(8-0)))} := \frac{(5-(7-(9-1)))}{(4 \times ((6+(3^2)) \times (8-0)))} := \frac{(5 \times ((7 \times 9)+1))}{((4+6) \times (32 \times 80))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times (7 \times (9+1)))}{(((4+6)^3) \times (28-0))} := \frac{(5 \times (7+(9 \times 1)))}{(4 \times (((6 \times 3)+2) \times 80))} := \frac{(5 \times (7+(9+1)))}{((4+((6+3)^2)) \times 80)} \\
 &:= \frac{(5+(7 \times 9)+1))}{((4+(63+2)) \times 80)} := \frac{(5+(7-(9 \times 1)))}{((4-(6-32)) \times (8-0))} := \frac{(5+(7-(9+1)))}{((4 \times (6+32))+(8-0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5+(7-(9-1)))}{(4 \times ((6-(3+2)) \times 80))} := \frac{(5+(7+(9+1)))}{(4 \times (((6^3) \times 2)+(8-0)))} := \frac{(5+(7+(9-1)))}{(4 \times ((6-(3-2)) \times 80))} \\
 &:= \frac{(57-(9 \times 1))}{(4 \times ((6+(3 \times 2)) \times 80))} := \frac{(57-(9+1))}{((46+(3-2)) \times 80)} := \frac{(57-(9-1))}{(((4+(6-3))^2) \times 80)} \\
 &:= \frac{(57+(9 \times 1))}{(((4^{6-3})+2) \times 80)} := \frac{(57+(9-1))}{((4+(63-2)) \times 80)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{7824}{109536}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((7-(8-2)) \times 4)}{(1 \times (0+(9+(53-6))))} := \frac{((7 \times (8-2))+4)}{(10-(95-(3^6)))} := \frac{((7 \times (8-2))-4)}{(1-(0-(9 \times (53+6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 \times 8)-(2^4))}{(10 \times (9+(53-6)))} := \frac{((7 \times 8)-(2+4))}{(10 \times (((9-5)^3)+6))} := \frac{((7+8) \times (2+4))}{(10 \times (9 \times (5+(3+6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7+8) \times 24)}{(10 \times ((9+5) \times 36))} := \frac{((7-8) \times (2-4))}{(1-(0-((9 \times 5)-(3 \times 6))))} := \frac{(7-(8-(2 \times 4)))}{(1 \times (0+(95-(3-6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7-(8-(2^4)))}{((1+09) \times ((5 \times 3)+6))} := \frac{(7-(8-(2+4)))}{(1 \times (0+(((9-5)^3)+6)))} := \frac{(7-(8+(2-4)))}{(1-(0-(9-(5-(3+6)))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 \times ((8^2)-4))}{(10 \times ((95+3) \times 6))} := \frac{(7 \times (8-(2-4)))}{(10 \times (95-(3-6)))} := \frac{(7 \times (8+(2-4)))}{(1 \times (0+((95+3) \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7+((8 \times 2)+4))}{((1-(0-(9+53))) \times 6)} := \frac{(7+((8 \times 2)-4))}{((10+9) \times (5+(3+6)))} := \frac{(7+(8-(2+4)))}{(1 \times (0+(9 \times (5+(3+6)))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7+(8 \times (2^4)))}{(10 \times (9+(5 \times 36)))} := \frac{(7+(8 \times (2+4)))}{(10 \times (95-(3 \times 6)))} := \frac{(7+(8+(2+4)))}{(((1-(0-95)) \times 3)+6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7+(8+24))}{(1-(0-(9+536)))} := \frac{(7+(82-4))}{((1+09) \times ((5^3)-6))} := \frac{(78-(2-4))}{(1-(0-((9 \times (5^3))-6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(78 \times (2+4))}{((1095-3) \times 6)} := \frac{(78-24)}{(((1^{09})+(5^3)) \times 6)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{9765}{312480}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((9-7) \times 6)-5)}{((3+(1+24)) \times (8-0))} := \frac{((9-(7-6)) \times 5)}{(((3-(1^2))^4) \times 80)} := \frac{((9-(7-6))^5)}{(((3+1)^2) \times (4^8+0))} \\
 &:= \frac{((9 \times 7)-(6-5))}{(31 \times (2 \times (4 \times (8-0))))} := \frac{((9 \times 7)+(6 \times 5))}{(3 \times (124 \times (8-0)))} := \frac{((9 \times 7)+(6-5))}{(((3+(1^2))^4) \times (8-0))} \\
 &:= \frac{((9 \times 7)+65)}{((3+1)^{2-4+8+0})} := \frac{((9+(7-6)) \times 5)}{((3+(1+(2^4))) \times 80)} := \frac{((9-7) \times (6 \times 5))}{(3 \times (1 \times (2 \times (4 \times 80))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((9-7) \times (6^5))}{(3 \times ((12^4) \times (8-0)))} := \frac{(9-((7-6) \times 5))}{((3 \times (1 \times (2^4))) + 80)} := \frac{(9-((7-6)^5))}{((3+(1+(2-4)))^8+0)} \\
 &:= \frac{(9-(7-(6+5)))}{((31 \times (2^4))-80)} := \frac{(9-(7-(6-5)))}{(3 \times (1 \times (24+(8-0))))} := \frac{(9-(7 \times (6-5)))}{((3 \times (1 \times 24))-(8-0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9-(7+(6-5)))}{(3-(1+(2-(4 \times (8-0)))))} := \frac{(9 \times ((7-6) \times 5))}{((3-(1-(2^4))) \times 80)} := \frac{(9 \times (7-(6-5)))}{(3 \times (12 \times (48-0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9^{(7-6)^5})}{(3 \times (1 \times (2 \times (48-0))))} := \frac{(9+((7-6)^5))}{(3-(1+(2-(4 \times 80))))} := \frac{(9+(7-(6+5)))}{((3+(1+(2^4))) \times (8-0))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(9 + (7 - (6 - 5)))}{(3 - (1 + (2 - 480)))} &:= \frac{(9 + (7 \times (6 - 5)))}{(((3 - 1)^{2+4}) \times (8 - 0))} &:= \frac{(9 + (7 + (6 + 5)))}{((3 \times (1 + 2)) \times (4 \times (8 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 + (76 + 5))}{(3 \times (1 \times (2 \times 480)))} &:= \frac{(9 + (76 - 5))}{(((3 \times 12) - 4) \times 80)} \end{aligned}$$

3.26 27 Equivalent Blocks

► $\frac{26710}{93485}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{((2 - (6 - 7)) \times 10)}{((9 - (3 \times (4 - 8))) \times 5)} &:= \frac{((2 \times (6 \times 7)) + 10)}{((9 \times (3 \times (4 + 8))) + 5)} &:= \frac{((2 \times 67) + 10)}{(9 \times (3 + (48 + 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{((2 + (6 + 7)) \times 10)}{((9 + (3 \times (4 \times 8))) \times 5)} &:= \frac{((2 + (6 - 7)) \times 10)}{(((9 + 3) \times 4) - (8 + 5))} &:= \frac{((2 + 6) \times (7 - (1 - 0)))}{(9 + (3 \times (48 + 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{((26 - 7) \times 10)}{((9^3) - (4^{8-5}))} &:= \frac{(2 - ((6 - 7) \times 10))}{(9 - (3 + (4 - (8 \times 5))))} &:= \frac{(2 - (6 - (7 - (1 - 0))))}{(9 - (3 - (4 - (8 - 5))))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (6 - (7 + (1 - 0))))}{(9 - ((3 + (4 - 8)) \times 5))} &:= \frac{(2 - (6 \times (7 - 10)))}{(2 - (6 \times (7 - 10)))} &:= \frac{(2 \times ((6 \times 7) - (1 - 0)))}{(2 \times ((93 \times 4) - 85))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (6 - (7 - 10)))}{((9 + (3 \times 4)) \times (8 - 5))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (6 \times (7 - (1 - 0))))}{(9 - (3 \times (4 - 85)))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (6 + (7 - (1 - 0))))}{(9 + ((3 + (4 + 8)) \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (6 + (7 \times (1 - 0))))}{((9 \times 3) + (4^{8-5}))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (6 + (7 - 10)))}{(9 + (3 - (4 - (8 + 5))))} &:= \frac{(2^{6+7-10})}{((9 \times 3) + (4 - (8 - 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + ((6 \times 7) + 10))}{(9 \times (3 \times (4 + (8 - 5))))} &:= \frac{(2 + (6 \times (7 - (1 - 0))))}{(((9 + (3 + 4)) \times 8) + 5)} &:= \frac{(2 + (6 \times (7 \times (1 - 0))))}{(9 - ((3 - (4 \times 8)) \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (6 \times (7 + (1 - 0))))}{((9 + (34 - 8)) \times 5)} &:= \frac{(2 + (6 + (7 - (1 - 0))))}{(26 \times (7 + (1 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(2 + (6 + (7 \times 10)))}{(934 - (8 - 5))} \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{27018}{94563}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{((2 \times (7 - (0 - 1))) + 8)}{((9 \times (4 + 5)) + (6 - 3))} &:= \frac{((2 \times (7^{01})) - 8)}{(9 + (4 + (5 + (6 - 3))))} &:= \frac{((2 \times (7 + (0 - 1))) + 8)}{((9 - 4) \times (5 + (6 + 3)))} \\ &:= \frac{((2 \times (70 \times 1)) - 8)}{(9 + (456 - 3))} &:= \frac{((2 + (7 - 0)) \times 18)}{(9 \times (4 + (56 + 3)))} &:= \frac{((2 - 7) \times (0 - (1 \times 8)))}{(((9 + 4) \times (5 + 6)) - 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (7 \times (0 \times 18)))}{(9 - (4 - (5 - (6 - 3))))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (7 - (0 - (1 \times 8))))}{((9 - (4 - (5 \times 6))) \times 3)} &:= \frac{(2 \times (7 - (0 - (1^8))))}{(9 + ((4 \times (5 + 6)) + 3))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (7 - (0 \times 18)))}{(94 - (5 \times (6 + 3)))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (7 \times (0 + (1 + 8))))}{(9 \times (4 + (5 \times (6 + 3))))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (7 \times (0 + 18)))}{(945 - 63)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (7 + (0 - (1^8))))}{((9 + (4 - (5 - 6))) \times 3)} &:= \frac{(2 \times (7 + (0 - (1 - 8))))}{(94 - (5 - (6 + 3)))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (70 - (1^8)))}{((9 \times ((4 + 5) \times 6)) - 3)} \\ &:= \frac{(2^{7-01^8})}{(9 + (4 - (5 - (6^3))))} &:= \frac{(2 + ((7 - (0 - 1)) \times 8))}{((9 \times ((4 \times 5) + 6)) - 3)} &:= \frac{(2 + (7 - (0 - (1^8))))}{(94 - (56 + 3))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (7 - (0 - (1 + 8))))}{(9 - (4 + (5 - 63)))} &:= \frac{(2 + (7 + (0 - (1^8))))}{(9 + (4 + (5 \times (6 - 3))))} &:= \frac{(2 + (70 + 18))}{(94 + (5 + (6^3)))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (70 - 18))}{(9 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 3))))} &:= \frac{(27 - (0 - (1 + 8)))}{(9 + ((4 \times (5 \times 6)) - 3))} &:= \frac{(27 + (0 - (1^8)))}{(94 + ((5 - 6) \times 3))} \\ &:= \frac{(270 \times (1 + 8))}{(945 \times (6 + 3))} &:= \frac{(270 \times 18)}{(945 \times (6 \times 3))} &:= \frac{(270 + 18)}{(945 + 63)} \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{27918}{46530}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(((2 \times 7) + 9) \times 18)}{(46 \times (5 \times (3 - 0)))} &:= \frac{((2 \times (7 \times (9 - 1))) + 8)}{((46 \times 5) - 30)} &:= \frac{((2 \times (7 + (9 \times 1))) - 8)}{(4 + (6^{5-3} + 0))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((2 \times 7) + (9 - (1 \times 8)))}{(4 + (6 + (5 \times (3 - 0))))} := \frac{((2 + (7 + (9 \times 1))) \times 8)}{(4 \times ((6 \times 5) + 30))} := \frac{((2 + (7 + 9)) \times 18)}{(4 + (6 + 530))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (7 - ((9 + 1) \times 8)))}{((4 + (6 - 5))^3 + 0)} := \frac{(2 - (7 - (9 - (1^8))))}{(4 + ((6 - 5)^3 + 0))} := \frac{(2 \times ((7 \times (9 + 1)) + 8))}{((46 \times 5) + 30)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((7 \times (9 - 1)) - 8))}{(4 + (6 + (5 \times 30)))} := \frac{(2 \times (7 - (9 - (1 \times 8))))}{(((4 - 6) \times 5) + 30)} := \frac{(2 \times (7 + ((9 + 1) \times 8)))}{((4 \times 65) + 30)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (7 + (9 - (1^8))))}{((4 - 6) \times (5 - 30))} := \frac{(2 \times (7 + (9 + (1 \times 8))))}{((4 + 6) \times (5 + (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(2 + ((7 + (9 + 1)) \times 8))}{((4 \times 65) - 30)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (7 - (9 - (1 + 8))))}{((4 + (6 - 5)) \times (3 - 0))} := \frac{(2 + (7 \times (9 + (1^8))))}{(4 \times ((6 - 5) \times 30))} := \frac{(2 + (7 + (9 \times (1 \times 8))))}{(4 + (6 + (5^3 + 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (7 + (9 \times (1 + 8))))}{((4 + (6 - 5)) \times 30)} := \frac{(2 + (7 + (9 + (1 + 8))))}{(4 + (6 + (5 + 30)))} := \frac{(2 + (791 + 8))}{(4 + ((6 + 5)^3 + 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(27 \times ((9 + 1) \times 8))}{(4 \times (6 \times (5 \times 30)))} := \frac{(27 \times (9 - (1^8)))}{(4 \times (6 \times (5 \times (3 - 0))))} := \frac{(27 \times (9 + (1^8)))}{((4 + (6 + 5)) \times 30)} \\
 &:= \frac{(27 + (9 + 18))}{((4 - (6 - 5)) \times 30)} := \frac{(279 + 18)}{(465 + 30)} := \frac{(279 - 18)}{(465 - 30)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{29180}{36475}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((2 \times 9) + 1) \times (8 - 0))}{((3 \times 64) - (7 - 5))} := \frac{(((2 \times 9) - 1) \times (8 - 0))}{((3 + ((6 \times 4) + 7)) \times 5)} := \frac{((2 \times (9 + 1)) + (8 - 0))}{((3 - (6 - 4)) \times (7 \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (9 + 1)) + 80)}{((3 - (6 - (4 \times 7))) \times 5)} := \frac{((2 \times (9 - 1)) - (8 - 0))}{(((3^{6-4}) - 7) \times 5)} := \frac{((2 \times (9 - 1)) + (8 - 0))}{((3 + (6 + (4 - 7))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^9 \times 1) + (8 - 0))}{((3^6) - (4 + 75))} := \frac{((2^9) - 180)}{((36 + 47) \times 5)} := \frac{((2 + (9 - 1)) \times (8 - 0))}{((3 + (6 + (4 + 7))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((29 + 1) \times (8 - 0))}{((3 + (64 - 7)) \times 5)} := \frac{((29 + 1) \times 80)}{((36 + 4) \times 75)} := \frac{((29 - 1) \times (8 - 0))}{((3 + (6 + 47)) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((9 - 1) \times 80))}{((36 + 4)^{7-5})} := \frac{(2 \times (9 - (1 - (8 - 0))))}{(3 + (6 - (4 - (7 \times 5))))} := \frac{(2 \times (9 - (1^8 + 0)))}{(3 - (6 - ((4 \times 7) - 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (9 - (1 - 80)))}{((3 - (6 - 47)) \times 5)} := \frac{(2 \times (9 \times (1 \times (8 - 0))))}{((3 \times 64) - (7 + 5))} := \frac{(2 \times (9 + (1^8 + 0)))}{(3 + (6 + (4^{7-5})))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (9 + (1 + (8 - 0))))}{(3 - (6 - (4 \times (7 + 5))))} := \frac{(2 \times (9 + (1 + 80)))}{(3 \times (((6 + 4) \times 7) + 5))} := \frac{(2^{9-1^8+0})}{((36 + (4 \times 7)) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2^{9+1-8+0})}{(3 - (6 - (4 \times (7 - 5))))} := \frac{(2 + (9 \times (18 - 0)))}{((3 \times ((6 + 4) \times 7)) - 5)} := \frac{(2 + (9 + (1^8 + 0)))}{(3 + (6 \times (4 - (7 - 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (9 + (1 + 80)))}{(((3 \times (6 + 4)) - 7) \times 5)} := \frac{(29 - (1 - 80))}{(3 \times (6 + (4 + (7 \times 5))))} := \frac{(29 \times (1 \times (8 - 0)))}{(3 + ((6 \times 47) + 5))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{32589}{76041}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (2 \times (5 + 8))) - 9)}{(7 \times ((6 \times (0 + 4)) - 1))} := \frac{((3 \times (2^5)) + (8 \times 9))}{(7 \times (60 - (4 \times 1)))} := \frac{((3 \times (2 + 58)) + 9)}{(7 \times (60 + (4 - 1)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times 25) - (8 \times 9))}{(7 - (6 \times (0 \times 41)))} := \frac{((3 \times 25) + (8 \times 9))}{(7^{6-0+1})} := \frac{((3 + (2 + 5)) \times (8 \times 9))}{(7 \times (60 \times (4 \times 1)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 + (25 + 8)) \times 9)}{(760 - (4 \times 1))} := \frac{(3 - (2 \times ((5 - 8) \times 9)))}{(7 \times (60 - 41))} := \frac{(3 - (2 \times (5 - (8 + 9))))}{(7 \times (6 - (0 - (4 - 1))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (2 \times (5 - 89)))}{(7 \times (60 - (4 - 1)))} := \frac{(3 - (2 + (5 \times (8 - 9))))}{(7 \times (6 + (0 - (4 \times 1))))} := \frac{(3 \times ((2^5) - 8) \times 9)}{(7 \times (6^{0+1}))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (((2 + 5) \times 8) + 9))}{(7 \times (60 + (4 + 1)))} := \frac{(3 \times (((2 + 5) \times 8) - 9))}{(7 \times (6 - (0 - 41)))} := \frac{(3 \times ((2 \times 5) - (8 - 9)))}{(7 \times (6 - (0 - (4 + 1))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (2 - (5 \times (8 - 9))))}{(7^{6-04 \times 1})} := \frac{(3 \times (2^{5-8+9}))}{(7 \times (60 + (4 \times 1)))} := \frac{(3 \times (2 + (5 + (8 + 9))))}{(7 \times (6 \times (0 + (4 \times 1))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (2 + (5 + (8 - 9))))}{(7 - (6 + (0 - 41)))} := \frac{(3 + (((2 \times 5) + 8) \times 9))}{(7 \times (60 - (4 + 1)))} := \frac{(3 + ((2 \times 5) + (8 + 9)))}{(7 \times (6 - (0 - (4 \times 1))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (2 \times (5 - (8 - 9))))}{(7 \times (6 + ((0 \times 4) - 1)))} := \frac{(3 + (2 \times (5 \times (8 \times 9))))}{(7 \times ((60 \times 4) + 1))} := \frac{(3 + (2 + (5 \times (8 + 9))))}{(7 \times (6 \times (0 + (4 + 1))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (2 + (5 + (8 - 9))))}{(7 \times (6 + (0 - (4 - 1))))} := \frac{(3 + (2 + (58 - 9)))}{(7 \times (6 \times (0 + (4 - 1))))} := \frac{3 + 2589}{7 + 6041}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{32876}{41095}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((3 \times 2) + 8) \times 7) - 6}{((4 + (10 + 9)) \times 5)} := \frac{(((3 \times 2) + 8) \times 76)}{((4 + 10) \times 95)} := \frac{((3 \times (2 \times 8)) + 76)}{(((4 \times 10) - 9) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (2 + (8 \times 7))) + 6)}{((4 + (1 - 0)) \times (9 \times 5))} := \frac{((3 \times 2) + ((8 \times 7) + 6))}{((4 \times 10) + (9 \times 5))} := \frac{((3 \times 2) + (8 + (7 \times 6)))}{((4 + (1 + 09)) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times 28) + 76)}{(4 \times ((1 + 09) \times 5))} := \frac{((3^2) + (8 - (7 - 6)))}{(4 \times (1 - (0 - (9 - 5))))} := \frac{((3 + (28 + 7)) \times 6)}{((4 - (1 - 0)) \times 95)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 + (28 - 7)) \times 6)}{(4 \times (1 \times (0 + (9 \times 5))))} := \frac{((3 - 2) \times (8 \times (7 \times 6)))}{(4 \times (10 + 95))} := \frac{((32 + 8) \times 76)}{(4 \times (10 \times 95))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (2 - (8 - (7 - 6))))}{(4 + ((1^{09}) + 5))} := \frac{(3 \times (2 - (8 - (7 \times 6))))}{((4 \times 10) + 95)} := \frac{(3 \times (2 \times ((8 - 7) \times 6)))}{((4 \times (1 + 09)) + 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (2 \times (8 \times (7 - 6))))}{(4 \times (1 - (0 - (9 + 5))))} := \frac{(3 \times (2 \times (8 + 76)))}{((4 + 10) \times (9 \times 5))} := \frac{(3 + ((2 \times 8) + (7 - 6)))}{((4 + (1^{09})) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + ((2^8) + (7 + 6)))}{(4 \times ((10 \times 9) - 5))} := \frac{(3 + (2 - ((8 - 7)^6)))}{(4 + (1 - (0 \times 95)))} := \frac{(3 + (2 + (8 - (7 - 6))))}{((4 - (1^{09})) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (28 + (7 + 6)))}{(41 - (0 - (9 + 5)))} := \frac{(3 + (28 + (7 - 6)))}{((4 + (1 - 0)) \times 9) - 5)} := \frac{(3 + (287 - 6))}{((4 \times (10 \times 9)) - 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(32 + (8 \times (7 - 6)))}{(4 + (1 - (0 - (9 \times 5))))} := \frac{328 + 76}{410 + 95} := \frac{328 - 76}{410 - 95}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{37528}{46910}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((3 \times 7) - 5)^2) + 8}{(((4 \times 6) + 9) \times 10)} := \frac{(((3 \times (7 - 5)) + 2) \times 8)}{((4 + 6) \times (9 - (1 - 0)))} := \frac{(((3 \times 7) + (5^2)) \times 8)}{(46 \times (9 + (1 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((3 \times 7) + 5) \times 28)}{(4 + 6) \times (91 - 0)} := \frac{(((3^7) - (5 - 2)) \times 8)}{(4 \times (6 \times 910))} := \frac{(((3 + 7)^{5+2}) \times 8)}{((4 + 6)^{9-1+0})} \\
 &:= \frac{(((37 + 5) \times 2) + 8)}{((4 \times 6) + (91 - 0))} := \frac{((3 - (7 - (5 \times 2))) \times 8)}{(4 \times (6 + (9 \times (1 - 0))))} := \frac{((3 \times ((7 + 5)^2)) + 8)}{(4 + (6 \times (91 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (7 - (5 + 2))) + 8)}{(4 - (6 \times (9 - 10)))} := \frac{((3 \times (7 - (5 - 2))) - 8)}{((4 \times 6) - (9 + 10))} := \frac{((3^7) + (5 + (2 \times 8)))}{(4 \times (69 \times 10))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 + (7 \times (5 \times 2))) \times 8)}{((4 + 69) \times 10)} := \frac{((3 + (7 \times (5 - 2))) \times 8)}{(4 \times (6 \times (9 + (1 - 0))))} := \frac{((37 + (5 \times 2)) \times 8)}{(469 + (1 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - ((7 \times 5) - (2^8)))}{(4 \times (69 + (1 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 - (7 - ((5 + 2) \times 8)))}{(46 + (9 + 10))} := \frac{(3 - (7 - ((5 - 2) \times 8)))}{((4 \times 6) - (9 - 10))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (7 - (52 + 8)))}{((4 - (6 - 9)) \times 10)} := \frac{(3 \times (7 - (5 - (2 + 8))))}{(46 + (9 - 10))} := \frac{(3 \times (7 + ((5^2) - 8)))}{((4 + 6) \times (9 \times (1 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (7 + (5 + 28)))}{(((4 \times 6) - 9) \times 10)} := \frac{(3 + ((7 \times (5 + 2)) - 8))}{(46 + (9 \times (1 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 + ((7 \times (5 - 2)) - 8))}{(4 \times (6 + (9 - 10)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (7 - (5 \times (2 - 8))))}{((4 \times (6 + 9)) - 10)} := \frac{(3 + (7 \times (5 - (2 - 8))))}{(4 \times (6 + (9 + 10)))} := \frac{(3 + (7 + ((5 \times 2) - 8)))}{((4 \times 6) - (9 \times (1 - 0)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{47136}{58920} &:= \frac{((4 \times (7 + (1^3)))^6)}{(5 \times ((8^9) \times (2 - 0)))} := \frac{((4 + (7 + (1 \times 3))) \times 6)}{(5 + (8 + (92 - 0)))} := \frac{((47 - (1^3)) \times 6)}{(5 \times (89 - 20))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (7 - (13 - 6)))}{(5^{8-9+2+0})} := \frac{(4 - (7 + (1 - 36)))}{(58 - (9 \times (2 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times (((7 + 1)^3)^6))}{(5 \times ((8^9)^2 + 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times ((7 \times (1 + 3)) + 6))}{(5 \times ((8 + 9) \times (2 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times ((7 + (1 - 3)) \times 6))}{(58 + (92 - 0))} := \frac{(4 \times ((7 + 1) \times (3 \times 6)))}{(5 \times (8 \times (9 \times (2 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (7 - ((1 - 3) \times 6)))}{(5 \times (8 - (9 - 20)))} := \frac{(4 \times (7 - (1 - (3 \times 6))))}{((5 - (8 - 9)) \times 20)} := \frac{(4 \times (7 - (1 - (3 + 6))))}{(5 \times (8 + (9 - (2 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (7 - (1 - (3 - 6))))}{(5 - (8 - (9 \times (2 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 \times (7 \times (1 + (3 + 6))))}{(5 \times ((8 \times 9) - (2 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times (7 + ((1^3) \times 6)))}{((5 \times (8 + 9)) - 20)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (7 + (1 \times (3^6))))}{(5 \times (8 \times (92 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times (7 + (1 \times (3 - 6))))}{(5 + (8 + (9 - (2 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 \times (7 + (1 + (3 \times 6))))}{(5 \times (8 + (9 \times (2 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (7 + (1 + (3 - 6))))}{(5 - ((8 - 9) \times 20))} := \frac{(4 \times (7 + (1 + 36)))}{((5 \times 8) + (9 \times 20))} := \frac{(4 \times (7 + (13 \times 6)))}{((5 \times 89) - 20)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (71 - (3 - 6)))}{(5 \times ((8 \times 9) + (2 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times (71 + (3 \times 6)))}{(5 \times (8 + (9^2 + 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times (71 + (3 - 6)))}{((5 \times (8 \times 9)) - 20)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4^{7-1+3-6})}{((5 + (8 - 9)) \times 20)} := \frac{(4 + ((7 + 1) \times (3 \times 6)))}{(5 \times (8 + (9 + 20)))} := \frac{(4 + 7136)}{(5 + 8920)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{60195}{84273} &:= \frac{(((6 \times (0 - 1)) + 9) \times 5)}{((8 + (4 + (2 - 7))) \times 3)} := \frac{(((6 + (0 - 1)) \times 9) - 5)}{(8 + (4 \times (2 + (7 + 3))))} := \frac{((6 - (0 - (1 \times 9))) \times 5)}{(((8 - 4) \times 27) - 3)} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 - (0 - (1^9))) \times 5)}{((8 \times 4) + ((2 \times 7) + 3))} := \frac{((6 \times (0 \times 1)) + (9 \times 5))}{((8 + (4 + (2 + 7))) \times 3)} := \frac{((6 \times (0 \times 1)) + 95)}{(8 + (((4 - 2)^7) - 3))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 \times (0 + (1 + 9))) - 5)}{(8 - ((4 - 27) \times 3))} := \frac{((6 + (0 - (1^9))) \times 5)}{(8 + (4 + (2 + (7 \times 3))))} := \frac{((6 + (0 - 1)) \times (9 \times 5))}{((8 \times 42) - (7 \times 3))} \\
 &:= \frac{((60 + (1 \times 9)) \times 5)}{(((84 \times 2) - 7) \times 3)} := \frac{(6 - (0 - (1 \times (9 + 5))))}{(8 + (4 + (2^7 - 3)))} := \frac{(6 - (0 - (1 \times (9 - 5))))}{(8 + (4 - (2 - (7 - 3))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (0 - ((1 - 9) \times 5)))}{(8 \times ((4 - 2) \times (7 \times 3)))} := \frac{(6 \times (0 + ((1 + 9) \times 5)))}{((8 + (4 + (2^7))) \times 3)} := \frac{(6 \times (0 + (1 + (9 + 5))))}{((8 - (4 - 2)) \times (7 \times 3))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (0 + (1 + (9 - 5))))}{(8 + (4 + (27 + 3)))} := \frac{(6 + (0 - (1^{95})))}{(8 - (((4 \times 2) - 7)^3))} := \frac{(6 + (0 - (1 - 95)))}{((8 + (4 + 2)) \times (7 + 3))} \\
 &:= \frac{(60 \times ((1^9) + 5))}{(8 \times (42 + (7 \times 3)))} := \frac{(60 \times (1 \times (9 + 5)))}{(8 \times ((42 + 7) \times 3))} := \frac{(60 \times (19 + 5))}{(84 \times (27 - 3))} \\
 &:= \frac{(60 \times (1^{95}))}{(8 - (4 \times (2 - (7 \times 3))))} := \frac{(60 + ((1 + 9) \times 5))}{(8 + ((4 - 2) \times 73))} := \frac{(60 + (1 \times (9 \times 5)))}{((8 \times (4 + (2 \times 7))) + 3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(60 + (1 \times 95))}{(((8 + 4)^2) + 73)} := \frac{(60 + 195)}{(8 + (4 + (2 + (7^3))))} := \frac{(601 + (9 + 5))}{((8 \times (4 \times 27)) - 3)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{75328}{94160} &:= \frac{(((7 - 5) \times 3)^2) \times 8)}{((9 - (4 - 1)) \times 60)} := \frac{(((7 \times (5 - 3))^2) + 8)}{(9 + (41 \times (6 - 0)))} := \frac{((7 - (5 - (3 \times 2))) \times 8)}{((9 - 4) \times (16 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 - (5 - (3^2))) \times 8)}{(9 + (41 + 60))} := \frac{((7 - (5 \times (3 - 2))) \times 8)}{(9 + (4 + (1 + (6 - 0))))} := \frac{((7 - (5 + (3 - 2))) \times 8)}{(9 - (4 + (1 - (6 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 - (5 - 3)) \times (2 \times 8))}{(94 + (1 \times (6 - 0)))} := \frac{((7 \times ((5 + 3)^2)) + 8)}{((94 + 1) \times (6 - 0))} := \frac{((7 + ((5 \times 3) + 2)) \times 8)}{((9 - (4 + 1)) \times 60)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 + (5 - (3^2))) \times 8)}{((9 - (4 \times 1)) \times (6 - 0))} := \frac{((7 + (5 + (3 \times 2))) \times 8)}{(9 \times (4 + (16 - 0)))} := \frac{((7 + (5 + 3)) \times (2 \times 8))}{((9 + 41) \times (6 - 0))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((7+5) \times (3 \times (2 \times 8)))}{((9+(4-1)) \times 60)} := \frac{((75+(3^2)) \times 8)}{((9+(4+1)) \times 60)} := \frac{((75+(3+2)) \times 8)}{((9-4) \times 160)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7-(5 \times (3-28)))}{(9-(4-160))} := \frac{(7 \times (5-((3^2)-8)))}{(94+(1-60))} := \frac{(7 \times (5-(3-(2+8))))}{((9 \times (4+1)) + 60)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 \times (5 \times (3 \times (2 \times 8))))}{(((9 \times 4)-1) \times 60)} := \frac{(7 \times (5+(3+(2 \times 8))))}{(((9 \times 4)-1) \times (6-0))} := \frac{(7 \times (5+(3+28)))}{(9 \times (41-(6-0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7+(5-((3-2) \times 8)))}{(9-(4 \times (1^6+0)))} := \frac{(7+(5 \times (3-(2-8))))}{(9-(4-(1 \times 60)))} := \frac{(7+(5 \times (3+(2+8))))}{(9 \times (4+(1 \times (6-0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7+(5+(32-8)))}{(9 \times (4+(1^6+0)))} := \frac{(7+(5+328))}{(9+(416-0))} := \frac{(7+(53+(2 \times 8)))}{(94+(1^6+0))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{2697}{134850}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((2 \times 6)-9) \times 7)}{((1+((3 \times 4)+8)) \times 50)} := \frac{((2-(6-9)) \times 7)}{(1 \times ((3+(4 \times 8)) \times 50))} := \frac{((2 \times (6+9)) + 7)}{((1+(3 \times (4+8))) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (6-9)) + 7)}{(1+(3+(4-(8-50))))} := \frac{((2 \times 6)^{9-7})}{(1 \times (3 \times (48 \times 50)))} := \frac{((2 \times 69) + 7)}{((1+(3 \times 48)) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^6)-(9+7))}{((1^3) \times (48 \times 50))} := \frac{((2^6) \times (9-7))}{((1+3) \times (4 \times (8 \times 50)))} := \frac{((2+(6+9)) \times 7)}{(1 \times ((3+4) \times 850))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2-(6-(9+7)))}{((1^3) \times ((4+8) \times 50))} := \frac{(2 \times (6-(9-7)))}{(1+(3-(4-(8 \times 50))))} := \frac{(2 \times (6 \times (9+7)))}{((1+3) \times (48 \times 50))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (6 \times (9-7)))}{(((1+3) \times 4)+8) \times 50)} := \frac{(2 \times (6^{9-7}))}{((13-4) \times (8 \times 50))} := \frac{(2 \times (6+(9+7)))}{(((13 \times 4)-8) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times 697)}{((1+(3^4)) \times 850)} := \frac{(2^{6-9+7})}{((1+(3+(4+8))) \times 50)} := \frac{(2^{6+9-7})}{(((1-(3-4))^8) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2+((6 \times 9)-7))}{(((1^3)+48) \times 50)} := \frac{(2+(6-(9-7)))}{(((13 \times 4)+8) \times (5-0))} := \frac{(2+(6+(9-7)))}{((1-(3-(4+8))) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2+(69-7))}{((1+(3+4)) \times (8 \times 50))} := \frac{(26 \times (9+7))}{(13 \times (4 \times (8 \times 50)))} := \frac{(26 \times (9-7))}{((1+(3+48)) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{(26+(9 \times 7))}{(1 \times (((3^4)+8) \times 50))} := \frac{(26+(9+7))}{(1 \times ((34+8) \times 50))} := \frac{(26+(9-7))}{((1+34) \times (8 \times (5-0)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{3942}{157680}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (9-4)) + 2)}{(((1^5)^7) \times 680)} := \frac{((3+(9+4)) \times 2)}{((15+(7-6)) \times 80)} := \frac{((3+9) \times (4 \times 2))}{(1 \times (5 \times (768-0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3+9) \times (4^2))}{((1^5) \times 7680)} := \frac{((3+9) \times (4+2))}{(((1+5) \times 7)-6) \times 80)} := \frac{((3+9) \times 42)}{((1+5) \times (7 \times (6 \times 80)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3+9)^{4-2})}{((1-(5-76)) \times 80)} := \frac{((39 \times 4)-2)}{(((1^5)+76) \times 80)} := \frac{((39+4) \times 2)}{(((1^5)+(7 \times 6)) \times 80)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3-(9-(4 \times 2)))}{(1 \times (5+(7+(68-0))))} := \frac{(3-(9-(4^2)))}{(1 \times (5 \times ((7-6) \times 80)))} := \frac{(3-(9-42))}{(1 \times ((5+(7+6)) \times 80))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times ((9 \times 4)+2))}{((15+(7 \times 6)) \times 80)} := \frac{(3 \times ((9 \times 4)-2))}{(1 \times ((57-6) \times 80))} := \frac{(3 \times ((9-4) \times 2))}{(15 \times ((7-6) \times 80))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (9 \times (4^2)))}{((1+(5 \times 7)) \times (6 \times 80))} := \frac{(3 \times (9 \times (4+2)))}{(1 \times ((5+76) \times 80))} := \frac{(3 \times (9+(4 \times 2)))}{((1-(5-7)) \times 680)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (94+2))}{(15 \times (768-0))} := \frac{(3^{9-4 \times 2})}{(15 \times ((7-6) \times (8-0)))} := \frac{(3+((9-4) \times 2))}{(1 \times (5 \times ((7+6) \times (8-0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3+(9-(4 \times 2)))}{((15-(7+6)) \times 80)} := \frac{(3+(9-(4+2)))}{((1+((5 \times 7)-6)) \times (8-0))} := \frac{(3+(9^{4-2}))}{((1+((5 \times 7)+6)) \times 80)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 + (9 + (4^2)))}{((15 - (7 - 6)) \times 80)} \quad := \frac{(3 + (9 + (4 + 2)))}{((1 - (5 - (7 + 6))) \times 80)} \quad := \frac{(3 + (9 + (4 - 2)))}{((1 + (5 + (7 - 6))) \times 80)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{4392}{175680} &:= \frac{(((4 \times 3) + 9) \times 2)}{(1 \times (7 \times (5 \times (6 \times (8 - 0)))))} \quad := \frac{(((4 \times 3) - 9) \times 2)}{((1 + ((7 \times 5) - 6)) \times (8 - 0))} \quad := \frac{(((4^3) + 9) \times 2)}{((1 + ((7 + 5) \times 6)) \times 80)} \\ &:= \frac{(((4 - 3)^9) \times 2)}{(1 \times (7 + (5 + (68 - 0))))} \quad := \frac{((4 - (3 - 9))^2)}{((1 - (7 - 56)) \times 80)} \quad := \frac{((4 \times 39) + 2)}{(((17 \times 5) - 6) \times 80)} \\ &:= \frac{((4 \times 39) - 2)}{(1 \times (7 \times ((5 + 6) \times 80)))} \quad := \frac{((4^3) + 92)}{((1 + (7 \times (5 + 6))) \times 80)} \quad := \frac{((4 + (3 \times 9)) \times 2)}{(((1^7) + (5 \times 6)) \times 80)} \\ &:= \frac{((4 + (3 + 9)) \times 2)}{((17 + (5 - 6)) \times 80)} \quad := \frac{((4 + 3) \times (9 \times 2))}{(1 \times ((7 + 56) \times 80))} \quad := \frac{((4 + 39) \times 2)}{((1 + 7) \times (5 \times (6 + 80)))} \\ &:= \frac{((4 - 3) \times (9 + 2))}{(((1 + 7) \times 56) - (8 - 0))} \quad := \frac{((4 - 3) \times 92)}{(((1 + 7) \times 5) + 6) \times 80)} \quad := \frac{((4 - 3)^{9-2})}{((1 - (7 - (5 + 6))) \times (8 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{((43 - 9) \times 2)}{((1 + 7) \times (5 \times (68 - 0)))} \quad := \frac{(4 - ((3 - 9) \times 2))}{(1 \times ((7 - (5 - 6)) \times 80))} \quad := \frac{(4 - (3 - (9^2)))}{(1 \times (((7 \times 5) + 6) \times 80))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - (3 - (9 + 2)))}{(1 \times ((7 + (5 - 6)) \times 80))} \quad := \frac{(4 - (3 - (9 - 2)))}{(((1 + 7) \times (5 \times 6)) + 80)} \quad := \frac{(4 \times (3 \times (9 - 2)))}{((1 + ((7 \times 5) + 6)) \times 80)} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (3 + (9 + 2)))}{((17 + (5 + 6)) \times 80)} \quad := \frac{(4 \times (39 + 2))}{((1 + (75 + 6)) \times 80)} \quad := \frac{(4 + (3 \times (9 \times 2)))}{(1 \times (((7 \times 5) - 6) \times 80))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + (3 + (9 + 2)))}{((1 + (7 - (5 - 6))) \times 80)} \quad := \frac{(4 + (3 + (9 - 2)))}{((1 + (7 + (5 - 6))) \times 80)} \quad := \frac{(43 - (9 - 2))}{(1 \times ((7 + (5 + 6)) \times 80))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{6729}{134580} &:= \frac{(((6 + 7)^2) - 9)}{((1 + (34 + 5)) \times 80)} \quad := \frac{((6 - (7 - 2)) \times 9)}{((13 \times (4 \times 5)) - 80)} \quad := \frac{((6 - (7 - 2))^9)}{(1 \times (3 + (4 + (5 + (8 - 0)))))} \\ &:= \frac{((6 \times 7) - 29)}{(((1 + 3) \times 45) + 80)} \quad := \frac{((6 + (7 \times 2)) \times 9)}{((13 - 4) \times (5 \times 80))} \quad := \frac{((6 + 7) \times (2 \times 9))}{(13 \times (45 \times (8 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{((6 + 7) \times 29)}{((1 + (3 \times 4)) \times 580)} \quad := \frac{((6 - 7) \times (2 - 9))}{((6 - 7) \times (2 - 9))} \quad := \frac{(6 - (7 - (2 \times 9)))}{((13 \times (4 \times 5)) + 80)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - (7 - (2 + 9)))}{(((1^3) + 4) \times (5 \times (8 - 0)))} \quad := \frac{(6 - (7 + (2 - 9)))}{(1 + (34 + (5 + 80)))} \quad := \frac{(6 - (7 - 29))}{((1 - (3 - (4 + 5))) \times 80)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times ((7 \times 2) + 9))}{(1 \times (345 \times (8 - 0)))} \quad := \frac{(6 \times ((7 \times 2) - 9))}{((1 - 3) \times (4 \times (5 - 80)))} \quad := \frac{(6 \times ((7^2) + 9))}{(1 \times (3 \times (4 \times 580)))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times ((7^2) - 9))}{(1 \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 80))))} \quad := \frac{(6 \times (7 - (2 - 9)))}{(((1^3) + (4 \times 5)) \times 80)} \quad := \frac{(6 \times (7 + (2 + 9)))}{(1 \times (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times 80)))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + ((7 \times 2) + 9))}{(1 + (3 - (4 - 580)))} \quad := \frac{(6 + ((7 - 2) \times 9))}{(1 \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 + 80))))} \quad := \frac{(6 + (7 - (2 + 9)))}{(1 + (3 - (4 - (5 \times (8 - 0)))))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + (7 - (2 - 9)))}{(1 + (3 - (4 - (5 \times 80))))} \quad := \frac{(6 + (7 \times (2 \times 9)))}{((13 + (4 \times 5)) \times 80)} \quad := \frac{(6 + (7 + (2 + 9)))}{(1 \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (8 - 0)))))} \\ &:= \frac{(67 - (2 + 9))}{((13 - (4 - 5)) \times 80)} \quad := \frac{(67 + (2 - 9))}{(((1 + 3)^4) \times 5) - 80)} \quad := \frac{(67 + 29)}{((1 + (3 + (4 \times 5))) \times 80)} \end{aligned}$$

3.27 28 Equivalent Blocks

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{17568}{43920} := \frac{(((1 + 7) \times 5) + 6) \times 8}{(4 - 3) \times 920} \quad := \frac{(((1 + 7) \times 5) - 6) \times 8}{(43 - 9) \times 20} \quad := \frac{((1 + 7) \times 56) - 8}{(((4^3) - 9) \times 20)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((1 - (7 - (5 + 6))) \times 8)}{((4 - (3 - 9))^2 + 0)} := \frac{((1^{756}) \times 8)}{((4 - (3 - 9)) \times (2 - 0))} := \frac{((1^7) - (5 - (6 \times 8)))}{((4 \times (3 \times 9)) + (2 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1^7) + (5 + (6 \times 8)))}{(43 + (92 - 0))} := \frac{((1 + ((7 + 5) \times 6)) \times 8)}{(((4^3) + 9) \times 20)} := \frac{((1 + (7 + (5 + 6))) \times 8)}{(4 \times (3 + (92 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((17 + (5 - 6)) \times 8)}{((4 + (3 + 9)) \times 20)} := \frac{(1 - (7 - (56 + 8)))}{((4^3) + (9^2 + 0))} := \frac{(1 - (7 + ((5 - 6) \times 8)))}{((4 \times 3) - (9 - (2 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (((7 - 5) \times 6) + 8))}{((4 \times (3 + 9)) + (2 - 0))} := \frac{(1 \times ((7 \times 56) - 8))}{(4 \times ((3 + 9) \times 20))} := \frac{(1 \times ((7 + 5) \times (6 + 8)))}{(((4 \times 3) + 9) \times 20)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((7 + 56) \times 8))}{(1 \times ((7 + 56) \times 8))} := \frac{(1 \times (7 - (5 - (6 + 8))))}{(1 \times (7 - (5 - (6 + 8))))} := \frac{(1 \times (7 \times ((5 \times 6) - 8)))}{(1 \times (7 \times ((5 \times 6) - 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 + 3) \times (9 \times 20))}{(1 \times (7 + (5 - (6 - 8))))} := \frac{((4 \times (3 + (9 - (2 - 0))))}{(1 \times (7 + (5 + (6 + 8))))} := \frac{((43 \times 9) - (2 - 0))}{(1 \times (7 + (5 + (6 - 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (7 + (5 - (6 - 8))))}{((4^3) - (9 + 20))} := \frac{(1 \times (7 + (5 + (6 + 8))))}{(((4 + 3) \times 9) + (2 - 0))} := \frac{(1 \times (7 + (5 + (6 - 8))))}{(4 + (3 \times (9 - (2 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (7 + (5 + 68)))}{((4 - (3 - 9)) \times 20)} := \frac{(1 + (7 - (5 \times (6 - 8))))}{(4 + (39 + (2 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + (7^{5+6-8}))}{((4 + 39) \times 20)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (7 + ((5 \times 6) - 8)))}{((4^3) - (9 - 20))} := \frac{(1 + (7 + (5 \times (6 \times 8))))}{((4 + (3 \times 9)) \times 20)} := \frac{(1 + (7 + (56 + 8)))}{((4 - 3) \times (9 \times 20))} \\
 &:= \frac{(17 + (5 - (6 - 8)))}{(((4 \times 3) - 9) \times 20)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► **25893**
60417

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((2 + 5) \times 8) + 9) \times 3}{((60 + (4 + 1)) \times 7)} := \frac{(((2 + 5) \times 8) - 9) \times 3}{((6 - (0 - 41)) \times 7)} := \frac{(((2^5) - 8) \times (9 \times 3))}{((6^{04-1}) \times 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 - (5 - 8)) \times (9 - 3))}{((6 - (0 - (4 \times 1))) \times 7)} := \frac{((2 \times (5 - (8 - 9))) + 3)}{((6 + ((0 \times 4) - 1)) \times 7)} := \frac{((2 \times (5 \times (8 \times 9))) + 3)}{(((60 \times 4) + 1) \times 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (5 \times (8 \times 9))) - 3)}{(((60 \times 4) - 1) \times 7)} := \frac{((2^{5-8+9}) \times 3)}{((60 + (4 \times 1)) \times 7)} := \frac{((2 + (5 - (8 - 9))) \times 3)}{(60 - (4 \times (1^7)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + 58) \times (9 + 3))}{(60 \times (4 \times (1 \times 7)))} := \frac{((2 - 5) \times (8 - (9 \times 3)))}{((60 - 41) \times 7)} := \frac{(2 \times ((5 - (8 - 9)) \times 3))}{(60 - (4 \times (1 - 7)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (5 - (8 - (9 + 3))))}{(6 \times ((0 \times 41) + 7))} := \frac{(2 \times (5 - (8 - (9 - 3))))}{((6 + (0 - (4 \times 1))) \times 7)} := \frac{(6 \times (0 + ((4 + 1) \times 7)))}{(2 + ((5 \times (8 + 9)) + 3))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + ((5 \times 8) + (9 \times 3)))}{(((6 \times (0 + 4)) - 1) \times 7)} := \frac{(2 + (5 \times (8 - (9 - 3))))}{(60 - (4 \times (1 + 7)))} := \frac{(2 + (5 \times (8 + (9 - 3))))}{(6 \times (0 + (4 \times (1 \times 7))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (5^{8-9+3}))}{((6 - (0 - (4 - 1))) \times 7)} := \frac{(2 + (5 + (8 - (9 + 3))))}{((6 \times (0 \times 41)) + 7)} := \frac{(2 + (5 + (8 - (9 - 3))))}{((6 + (0 - (4 - 1))) \times 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (5 + (8 + (9 - 3))))}{((6 - ((0 \times 4) - 1)) \times 7)} := \frac{(2 + (5 + 893))}{(60 \times ((4 + 1) \times 7))} := \frac{(2 + (58 - (9 \times 3)))}{(2 + (58 - (9 \times 3)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (58 - (9 - 3)))}{(6 \times (0 + (4 + 17)))} := \frac{(2589 + 3)}{(6041 + 7)} := \frac{(258 - 93)}{((60 - (4 + 1)) \times 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2589 - 3)}{(6041 - 7)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► **29385**
47016

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((2^9-3) - 8) \times 5)}{(4 \times (7 \times (0 + 16)))} := \frac{((2 \times (9 + (3 + 8))) + 5)}{((4 + (7 - (0 - 1))) \times 6)} := \frac{((2 \times (9 + (3 + 8))) - 5)}{(4 \times (7 - (0 - (1 + 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (9 - 3)) + (8 + 5))}{(4 + (((7 + (0 - 1)) \times 6))} := \frac{((2 \times (9 - 3)) + (8 - 5))}{(4 \times (7 + (0 - (1^6))))} := \frac{((2 \times (93 - 8)) - 5)}{((4 \times 70) - 16)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^9-3) \times (8 \times 5))}{(4^{7-016})} := \frac{((2^9) \times (3 \times (8 \times 5)))}{((4^{701}) \times 6)} := \frac{((2 + ((9 \times 3) + 8)) \times 5)}{((4 \times 70) + 16)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + ((9 \times 3) - 8)) \times 5)}{(4 \times (7 \times (0 + (1 \times 6))))} := \frac{((2 + (9 + (3 \times 8))) \times 5)}{(4 \times (70 \times (1^6)))} := \frac{((2 + (9 + (3 + 8))) \times 5)}{((4 + (7 - 0)) \times 16)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(2+938) \times 5}{(470 \times 16)} & := \frac{((29 - (3+8)) \times 5)}{(4 \times ((7 + (0-1)) \times 6))} & := \frac{((29 + (3 \times 8)) \times 5)}{(4 + (70 \times (1 \times 6)))} \\
 & := \frac{((29 + (3-8)) \times 5)}{(4 \times ((7 - (0-1)) \times 6))} & := \frac{(2 - (9 - (3^{8-5})))}{(4 \times (7 - (0 - (1^6))))} & := \frac{(2 - (9 \times (3 - 85)))}{((4 + 70) \times 16)} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times (((9 \times 3) - 8) \times 5))}{(4 \times (70 + (1 \times 6)))} & := \frac{(2 \times ((9 + 38) \times 5))}{(47 \times (0 + 16))} & := \frac{(2 \times (9 + (3 + (8 + 5))))}{(4 + (70 + (1 \times 6)))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times (9 + (3 + (8 - 5))))}{(4 \times (7 + (0 - (1 - 6))))} & := \frac{(2 \times (93 - (8 + 5)))}{(4 \times (70 - (1 \times 6)))} & := \frac{(2 + (9 - (3 + (8 - 5))))}{(4 \times (7 - (0 - (1 - 6))))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 + (93 + (8 \times 5)))}{(4 \times (70 - 16))} & := \frac{(2 + (93 + 85))}{((47 - (0 - 1)) \times 6)} & := \frac{(2 + (93 - 85))}{(4^{7+01-6})} \\
 & := \frac{(293 - (8 - 5))}{(470 - (1 \times 6))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{30195}{72468}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(((3 \times (0-1)) + 9) \times 5)}{((7 + ((2 \times 4) - 6)) \times 8)} & := \frac{((3 - (0 - (1 \times 9))) \times 5)}{(72 + (4 + 68))} & := \frac{((3 - (0 - (1^9))) \times 5)}{((7 - (2 + 4)) \times (6 \times 8))} \\
 & := \frac{((3 - (0 - 1)) \times (9 \times 5))}{((7 - (2 - 4)) \times (6 \times 8))} & := \frac{(((3 - (0 - 19)) \times 5)}{((7 + (2 + (4 \times 6))) \times 8)} & := \frac{((3 \times (0 \times 19)) + 5)}{((7 \times 2) - (4 + (6 - 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{((3 \times (0 + (1 + 9))) + 5)}{(7 \times (2 \times (4 - (6 - 8))))} & := \frac{((3 + (0 - (1^9))) \times 5)}{((7 - (2 - (4 - 6))) \times 8)} & := \frac{((3 + (0 - (1 - 9))) \times 5)}{((7 \times (2 \times (4 + 6))) - 8)} \\
 & := \frac{((3 + (0 - 1)) \times (9 \times 5))}{((7 + (2 \times (4 + 6))) \times 8)} & := \frac{((30 - (1 \times 9)) \times 5)}{(7 \times (2 \times (4 + (6 + 8))))} & := \frac{((30 - (1 + 9)) \times 5)}{((7 + (2 - 4)) \times (6 \times 8))} \\
 & := \frac{((30 \times (1 \times 9)) - 5)}{((7 \times (2 \times 46)) - 8)} & := \frac{((30 + (1 \times 9)) \times 5)}{((7 + 2) \times (4 + (6 \times 8)))} & := \frac{((30 + (1 + 9)) \times 5)}{(((7 \times 2) + 46) \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{((30 + 19) \times 5)}{(7 \times ((2 \times 46) - 8))} & := \frac{((30 - ((1 - 9) \times 5))}{(3 \times (0 - ((1 - 9) \times 5)))} & := \frac{(3 \times (0 + ((1 + 9) \times 5)))}{((7 - 2) \times (4 + 68))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (1 + (9 - 5))))}{((7 \times (2 - (4 - 6))) + 8)} & := \frac{(30 - ((1 - 9) \times 5))}{((7 + ((2 \times 4) + 6)) \times 8)} & := \frac{(30 \times (1 \times (9^5)))}{(((7 - (2 - 4))^6) \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{(30 \times (1 \times (9 + 5)))}{(7 \times (2 \times (4 + 68)))} & := \frac{(30 \times (1 + (9 \times 5)))}{((7 + 2) \times (46 \times 8))} & := \frac{(30 \times (19 + 5))}{((7 + 2) \times (4 \times (6 \times 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{(30 + ((1 + 9) \times 5))}{(((7 \times 2) + (4 + 6)) \times 8)} & := \frac{(30 + (1 \times (9 \times 5)))}{((7 \times (2^4)) + 68)} & := \frac{(30 + 195)}{(72 + 468)} \\
 & := \frac{(301 + (9 + 5))}{(7 \times (2 \times (46 + 8)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{32716}{40895}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(((3^2) \times 7) - 1) \times 6}{((4 - (0 - 89)) \times 5)} & := \frac{(((3 \times (2 + 7)) - 1) \times 6)}{((40 + (8 - 9)) \times 5)} & := \frac{((3 - (2 - 7)) \times 16)}{(40 \times (8 - (9 - 5)))} \\
 & := \frac{((3 - (2 - 71)) \times 6)}{((4 - (0 - 8)) \times (9 \times 5))} & := \frac{((3 \times (2 + 7)) - (1 + 6))}{((4 + (0 - (8 - 9))) \times 5)} & := \frac{((3 \times 27) + (1 - 6))}{((4 \times (0 \times 8)) + 95)} \\
 & := \frac{((3^2) \times ((7 + 1)^6))}{((4^{08}) \times (9 \times 5))} & := \frac{((3 + (2 \times 7)) \times 16)}{(4 \times (0 + ((8 + 9) \times 5)))} & := \frac{((32 + (7 - 1)) \times 6)}{((40 + (8 + 9)) \times 5)} \\
 & := \frac{(3 - (2 - (7 \times (1^6))))}{(4 + (0 - (8 - (9 + 5))))} & := \frac{(3 \times ((2^7-1) \times 6))}{(4 \times (0 + (8 \times (9 \times 5))))} & := \frac{(3 \times ((2^7) \times (1 + 6)))}{(40 \times (89 - 5))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 \times ((2 + (7 + 1)) \times 6))}{((40 \times 8) - 95)} & := \frac{(3 \times ((2 + (7 - 1)) \times 6))}{(4 \times ((0 \times 8) + (9 \times 5)))} & := \frac{(3 \times (2 \times (7 - (1^6))))}{((4 \times (0 \times 8)) + (9 \times 5))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 \times (2 \times (7 + (1 + 6))))}{((4 - (0 - (8 + 9))) \times 5)} & := \frac{(3 \times (2^{7 \times 1^6}))}{(40 \times (8 + (9 - 5)))} & := \frac{(3 + ((2 \times 7) - (1^6)))}{(4 \times ((0 \times 89) + 5))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(3 + (2 - (7 - (1 \times 6))))}{((4 \times (0 \times 89)) + 5)} := \frac{(3 + (2 + (7 \times (1^6))))}{((4 - (0 - (8 - 9))) \times 5)} := \frac{(3 + (2 + (7 + 16)))}{(40 + ((8 - 9) \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(32 \times (7 \times 16))}{(40 \times (8 \times (9 + 5)))} := \frac{(32 \times (7 + (1 + 6)))}{((40 + (8 \times 9)) \times 5)} := \frac{(32 \times (71 + 6))}{(40 \times ((8 \times 9) + 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(32^{7+1-6})}{(40 \times (8 \times (9 - 5)))} := \frac{(32 + 716)}{(40 + 895)} := \frac{(327 - (1 + 6))}{(40 + (8 \times (9 \times 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(327 - (1 - 6))}{((40 \times 8) + 95)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{35217}{80496}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((3^{5-2}) - 1) \times 7)}{((80 \times 4) + 96)} := \frac{(((3 + 5) \times 21) + 7)}{(8 \times (0 - (4 - (9 \times 6))))} := \frac{((3 \times (5 \times 21)) + 7)}{(8 \times (0 - (4 - 96)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3^{5-2 \times 1}) \times 7)}{(8 \times ((0 \times 4) + (9 \times 6)))} := \frac{((3 + (5 \times 21)) \times 7)}{(8 \times (0 + (4 \times (9 \times 6))))} := \frac{((3 + (5^{2-1})) \times 7)}{((8 \times (0 + 4)) + 96)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 + (5^2)) \times (1 + 7))}{(8 \times (0 + (4^{9-6})))} := \frac{((3 + (5 + 21)) \times 7)}{(8 \times (0 + (4 + (9 \times 6))))} := \frac{((3 + 5) \times 217)}{(8 \times (0 + 496))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (5 \times (2 \times (1 - 7))))}{(80 + (4^{9-6}))} := \frac{(3 \times (((5^2) - 1) \times 7))}{((8 - (0 - 4)) \times 96)} := \frac{(3 \times ((5 \times 21) + 7))}{(8 \times ((0 \times 4) + 96))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times ((5 + (2 \times 1)) \times 7))}{(8 \times (0 + ((4 \times 9) + 6)))} := \frac{(3 \times ((5 + (2 + 1)) \times 7))}{((8 + (0 - 4)) \times 96)} := \frac{(3 \times (5 \times ((2 - 1) \times 7)))}{(8 \times (0 - ((4 - 9) \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (5 \times (2 \times (1 \times 7))))}{(8 \times (0 + (4 \times (9 + 6))))} := \frac{(3 \times (5 \times (21 + 7)))}{(80 \times (4 \times (9 - 6)))} := \frac{(3 \times (5 + (2 \times (1^7))))}{(8 \times ((0 \times 49) + 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + ((5^{2 \times 1}) + 7))}{(80^{4-9+6})} := \frac{(3 + (5 - (2 - (1^7))))}{(80 - (4^{9-6}))} := \frac{(3 + (5 \times (2 + 17)))}{(8 - (0 - (4 \times (9 \times 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (5^2 \times 1^7))}{((8 + (0 - 4))^{9-6})} := \frac{(3 + (5 + (2 \times 17)))}{(8 \times (0 + (4 \times (9 - 6))))} := \frac{(35 \times ((2 - 1) \times 7))}{(80 \times (4 + (9 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(35 \times (2 + (1 + 7)))}{(8 \times (0 + (4 + 96)))} := \frac{(35 \times (2 + 17))}{(80 \times (4 + (9 + 6)))} := \frac{(35 + 217)}{(80 + 496)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3521 + 7)}{((80 + 4) \times 96)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{41896}{52370}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((4 - (1 - (8 + 9))) \times 6)}{(5 \times (23 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{((4 - (1 - (8 - 9)))^6)}{(5 + (2 + (3 + 70)))} := \frac{((4 \times 18) + 96)}{(5 \times (2 \times (3 \times (7 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 + (1 - (8 - 9))) \times 6)}{((5 \times 23) - 70)} := \frac{((41 \times 8) + 96)}{(523 + (7 - 0))} := \frac{(4 - (((1^8) - 9) \times 6))}{((5 \times (2 - 3)) + 70)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (1 \times (8 - 96)))}{(5 \times (2 + (3 \times (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 \times (((1 + 8) \times 9) - 6))}{(5 \times (2 + (3 + 70)))} := \frac{(4 \times ((1 + (8 \times 9)) \times 6))}{(5 - (2 - (3^7 + 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (1 - (8 - (9 \times 6))))}{((5^2) + (3 \times 70))} := \frac{(4 \times (1 - (8 - (9 + 6))))}{(5 - (2 - (37 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times (1 \times ((8 \times 9) + 6)))}{(5 \times ((2^3) + 70))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (1 \times (8 - (9 - 6))))}{(5 + (2 \times (3 + (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 \times (1 \times (8 + 96)))}{(52 \times (3 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times (1 + ((8 \times 9) + 6)))}{((5^2) + 370)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (1 + (8 - (9 - 6))))}{(5 \times (2 - (3 - (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 \times (1 + (8 \times (9 - 6))))}{(52 + (3 + 70))} := \frac{(4 \times (1 + (8 + (9 - 6))))}{(5 \times (2 + (3 + (7 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (1 + (8 + 96)))}{((5^2) \times (3 \times (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times (1 + (89 - 6)))}{((5 - (2 - 3)) \times 70)} := \frac{(4 \times (18 - (9 - 6)))}{(5 \times ((2^3) + (7 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (1^{896}))}{(5^{2^3-7+0})} := \frac{(4 + (1 - (8 - (9 + 6))))}{(52 - (37 - 0))} := \frac{(4 + (1 \times (8 \times (9 - 6))))}{(5 + (23 + (7 - 0)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(4 + (1 + (8 + (9 - 6))))}{(5 + ((2^3) + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 + (1 + (89 - 6)))}{((5 \times (2^3)) + 70)} := \frac{(4 + (18 + (9 \times 6)))}{((5 \times (2 + 3)) + 70)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + 1896)}{(5 + 2370)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{2967}{148350}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((2 \times 9) - 6) \times 7)}{(1 \times ((4 + 8) \times 350))} := \frac{((2 \times (9 \times 6)) + 7)}{(((14 \times 8) + 3) \times 50)} := \frac{((2 \times (9 + 6)) + 7)}{((1 + ((4 + 8) \times 3)) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (9 - 6)) + 7)}{((1 - ((4 - 8) \times 3)) \times 50)} := \frac{((2 \times 9) - (6 + 7))}{((1^4) \times ((8 - 3) \times 50))} := \frac{((2 \times 9) - (6 - 7))}{((14 + (8 - 3)) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^{9-6}) \times 7)}{((1^4) \times (8 \times 350))} := \frac{((2^{9-6}) + 7)}{(1 \times ((4 + (8 + 3)) \times 50))} := \frac{((2^{9-6}) - 7)}{(1 + (4 - (8 - (3 + 50))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^9) - (6 - 7))}{(((1^4) + (8^3)) \times 50)} := \frac{((2 - 9) \times (6 - 7))}{(14 \times ((8 - 3) \times (5 - 0)))} := \frac{((29 \times 6) - 7)}{((1^4) \times 8350)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (9 - (6 \times 7)))}{((1 - (4 - 8)) \times 350)} := \frac{(2 - (9 - (6 + 7)))}{(((1^4) + (8 - 3)) \times 50)} := \frac{(2 - (9 \times (6 - 7)))}{((1^4) \times ((8 + 3) \times 50))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((9 - 6) \times 7))}{((14 - 8) \times 350)} := \frac{(2 \times (9 - (6 - 7)))}{(1 \times (4 \times ((8 - 3) \times 50)))} := \frac{(2 \times (9 + (6 + 7)))}{(1 \times (4 \times ((8 + 3) \times 50)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (9 + (6 - 7)))}{((1 + (4 + (8 + 3))) \times 50)} := \frac{(2^{9+6-7})}{((1 + 4) \times ((8^3) \times (5 - 0)))} := \frac{(2 + ((9 \times 6) + 7))}{(((1^4) + 8) \times 350)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (9 - (6 - 7)))}{(((1^4) + (8 + 3)) \times 50)} := \frac{(2 + (9 + (6 + 7)))}{((1^4) \times (8 \times (3 \times 50)))} := \frac{(2 + (9 + (6 - 7)))}{((1 + (4 + (8 - 3))) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (96 - 7))}{((1 + (4 + 8)) \times 350)} := \frac{(29 - (6 - 7))}{((1 + ((4 \times 8) - 3)) \times 50)} := \frac{(29 + (6 - 7))}{(1 \times ((4 + (8 \times 3)) \times 50))} \\
 &:= \frac{(29 + 67)}{(1 \times (4 \times (8 \times (3 \times 50))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{5832}{104976}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((5 + 8) \times 3) + 2)}{(((10 \times (4 + 9)) - 7) \times 6)} := \frac{(((5 + 8) \times 3) - 2)}{((10 + (4 + 97)) \times 6)} := \frac{((5 \times (8 - 3)) - 2)}{((10 - (4 - (9 \times 7))) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 \times 8) - (3 \times 2))}{((1 - (0 - (4 + 97))) \times 6)} := \frac{((5 \times 8) - (3 - 2))}{((10 - 4) \times (9 \times (7 + 6)))} := \frac{((5 + (8 + 3)) \times 2)}{(((10 - 4) \times 97) - 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 + (8 - 3)) \times 2)}{((1 + (0 - (4 - (9 \times 7)))) \times 6)} := \frac{(5 - (8 - (3 \times 2)))}{((1 - (0 - (4 \times (9 - 7)))) \times 6)} := \frac{(5 - (8 - (3^2)))}{(1 - (0 - (4 + (97 + 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 - (8 - (3 + 2)))}{(1 \times (0 + (4 \times (9 \times (7 - 6))))} := \frac{(5 \times (8 - (3 \times 2)))}{((1 - (0 - ((4 \times 9) - 7))) \times 6)} := \frac{(5 \times (8 - (3 + 2)))}{((10 - ((4 - 9) \times 7)) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times (8 - (3 - 2)))}{((10 - (4 - 9)) \times (7 \times 6))} := \frac{(5 \times (8 \times (3 - 2)))}{((104 + (9 + 7)) \times 6)} := \frac{(5 + ((8 \times 3) + 2))}{(1 \times (0 - ((4 - 97) \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + ((8 + 3)^2))}{((10 - 4) \times (9 \times (7 \times 6)))} := \frac{(5 + (8 - (3 \times 2)))}{((1 - (0 - (4 + (9 + 7)))) \times 6)} := \frac{(5 + (8 - (3^2)))}{(1 - (0 - (4 - (9 - 76))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (8 - (3 + 2)))}{(((10 \times 4) - (9 + 7)) \times 6)} := \frac{(5 + (8 - (3 - 2)))}{((1 + (0 - ((4 - 9) \times 7))) \times 6)} := \frac{(5 + (8 \times (3 - 2)))}{((10 + ((4 \times 9) - 7)) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (8 + (3 \times 2)))}{((1 - (0 - (49 + 7))) \times 6)} := \frac{(5 + (8 + (3^2)))}{((10 + (49 + 7)) \times 6)} := \frac{(5 + (8 + (3 - 2)))}{(1 \times (0 + ((49 - 7) \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(58 - (3 \times 2))}{(104 \times (9 \times (7 - 6)))} := \frac{(58 + (3^2))}{((104 + 97) \times 6)} := \frac{(58 + (3 - 2))}{(1049 + (7 + 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(58 - 32)}{(1 \times (0 + (4 \times (9 \times (7 + 6))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{6297}{314850} &:= \frac{(((6 \times 2) + 9) \times 7)}{(3 \times ((1 + 48) \times 50))} &:= \frac{(((6 + 2) \times 9) + 7)}{((31 + 48) \times 50)} &:= \frac{(((6 - 2) \times 9) + 7)}{((3 + ((1 + 4) \times 8)) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 \times (2 \times 9)) + 7)}{((3 + (14 \times 8)) \times 50)} &:= \frac{((6 \times (2 + 9)) + 7)}{(((3 \times (1 \times 4)) - 8) \times 50)} &:= \frac{((6 \times 2)^{9-7})}{(3 \times (1 \times (48 \times 50)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 \times 2) + (9 - 7))}{((3 - (1 - (4 + 8))) \times 50)} &:= \frac{((6^2) - (9 - 7))}{((3 - (1 - (4 \times 8))) \times 50)} &:= \frac{((6^2) + (9 \times 7))}{(3 \times ((1 + (4 \times 8)) \times 50))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6^2) + (9 + 7))}{((3 + (1 + 48)) \times 50)} &:= \frac{((6 + (2 + 9)) \times 7)}{((3 + (1 \times 4)) \times 850)} &:= \frac{((6 + 2) \times (9 + 7))}{(((3 - 1)^4) \times (8 \times 50))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 - 2) \times (9 - 7))}{(3 + (1 - (4 - (8 \times 50))))} &:= \frac{((6 - 2) \times 97)}{((3 + 1) \times 4850)} &:= \frac{((6 - 2)^{9-7})}{((3 + (1 + (4 + 8))) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 - (2 - (9 + 7)))}{(((3 \times (1 \times 4)) + 8) \times 50)} &:= \frac{(6 - (2 - (9 - 7)))}{((3 - (1 + (4 - 8))) \times 50)} &:= \frac{(6 - (2^{9-7}))}{(3 - (1 - (48 + 50)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times ((2 \times 9) - 7))}{(3 \times ((14 + 8) \times 50))} &:= \frac{(6 \times (2 \times (9 + 7)))}{((3 + 1) \times (48 \times 50))} &:= \frac{(6 \times (2^{9-7}))}{(3 \times ((1^4) \times (8 \times 50)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (29 + 7))}{((31 - 4) \times (8 \times 50))} &:= \frac{(6 + ((2 \times 9) - 7))}{(3 + (1 - (4 - 850)))} &:= \frac{(6 + (2 \times (9 \times 7)))}{(((31 \times 4) + 8) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 + (2^{9-7}))}{((3 - ((1^4) - 8)) \times 50)} &:= \frac{(6 + (29 - 7))}{((31 + 4) \times (8 \times (5 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(62 \times (9 + 7))}{(31 \times (4 \times (8 \times 50)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(62 + (9 - 7))}{((3 + (1 + 4)) \times (8 \times 50))} & & &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7956}{318240} &:= \frac{(((7 + 9) \times 5) + 6)}{((3 + (1 + 82)) \times 40)} &:= \frac{((7 - (9 - 5)) \times 6)}{(3 \times (1 \times ((8 - 2) \times 40)))} &:= \frac{((7 - (9 - 5))^6)}{((3 \times (1 \times (8 - 2))) \times 40)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 \times (9 - 5)) + 6)}{(((3 + 1) \times 8) + 2) \times 40)} &:= \frac{((7 \times (9 - 5)) - 6)}{((3 + (1 \times 8)) \times (2 \times 40))} &:= \frac{((7 \times 9) - (5 \times 6))}{(3 \times ((1 + (8 + 2)) \times 40))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 \times 9) - (5 + 6))}{(((3 \times 18) - 2) \times 40)} &:= \frac{((7 \times 9) - (5 - 6))}{(((3 - 1)^{8-2}) \times 40)} &:= \frac{((7 \times 9) - 56)}{(318 + (2 - 40))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 + (9 + 5)) \times 6)}{((3 + 18) \times 240)} &:= \frac{((7 + (9 - 5)) \times 6)}{((3 - (1 - (8^2))) \times 40)} &:= \frac{((7 - 9) \times (5 - 6))}{(3 - (1 - (82 - (4 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 - (9 - (5 + 6)))}{((3 + (1 \times (8 - 2))) \times 40)} &:= \frac{(7 - (9 \times (5 - 6)))}{(((3 + (1^8))^2) \times 40)} &:= \frac{(7 - (9 - 56))}{(3 \times ((1 + 8) \times (2 \times 40)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 \times (9 + (5 - 6)))}{(((3 \times 18) + 2) \times 40)} &:= \frac{(7 + ((9 - 5) \times 6))}{(31 \times ((8 + 2) \times (4 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(7 + (9 - (5 + 6)))}{(3 + ((1^8) \times 2)) \times 40)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (9 - (5 - 6)))}{((3 - ((1 - 8) \times 2)) \times 40)} &:= \frac{(7 + (9 + (5 \times 6)))}{((31 - 8) \times (2 \times 40))} &:= \frac{(7 + (9 + (5 + 6)))}{((3^{1^8+2}) \times 40)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (9 + (5 - 6)))}{((31 - (8 \times 2)) \times 40)} &:= \frac{(7 + (9 + 56))}{((3 + (1 + 8)) \times 240)} &:= \frac{(7 + (95 + 6))}{(3 \times (18 \times (2 \times 40)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (95 - 6))}{((3 - 1) \times (8 \times 240))} &:= \frac{(79 - (5 + 6))}{((3 + (1 + (8^2))) \times 40)} &:= \frac{(79 + (5 - 6))}{((31 + 8) \times (2 \times 40))} \\
 &:= \frac{(79 - 56)}{(3 + (18 + 2)) \times 40)} & & &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9612}{307584} &:= \frac{((9 - (6 \times 1))^2)}{(3 \times (0 + (7 + (5 + 84))))} &:= \frac{((9 - (6 - 1)) \times 2)}{((3 - ((0 \times 7) - 5)) \times (8 \times 4))} &:= \frac{((9 \times (6 + 1)) + 2)}{((30 + (7 \times 5)) \times (8 \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{((9 \times 6) - 12)}{(((3 \times (0 + 7)) - 5) \times 84)} &:= \frac{((9 + (6 + 1)) \times 2)}{((30 + (7 - 5)) \times (8 \times 4))} &:= \frac{((9 + (6 - 1)) \times 2)}{((30^{7-5}) - (8 - 4))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(9 - (6 - (1 \times 2)))}{((3 - (0 - (7 - 5))) \times (8 \times 4))} := \frac{(9 - (6 - (1^2)))}{((30 + (7 - 5)) \times (8 - 4))} := \frac{(9 - (6 - (1 + 2)))}{(3 + (0 - (7 \times (5 - (8 \times 4))))))} \\
 & := \frac{(9 - (6 + (1 \times 2)))}{(3 + (0 - (7 - ((5 \times 8) - 4))))} := \frac{(9 - (6 + (1^2)))}{(3 - (0 - (7 + (58 - 4))))} := \frac{(9 - (6 - 12))}{((3 - (0 - (7 + 5))) \times (8 \times 4))} \\
 & := \frac{(9 \times ((6 - 1) \times 2))}{(30 \times (7 + (5 + 84)))} := \frac{(9 \times (6 - (1 \times 2)))}{(3 \times (0 + ((7 + 5) \times (8 \times 4))))} := \frac{(9 \times (6 - (1^2)))}{(30 \times ((7 + 5) \times (8 - 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{(9 \times (6 \times 12))}{((3 \times (0 + (7 + (5 - 8))))^4)} := \frac{(9 \times (6 \times (1 + 2)))}{(3 \times (0 + ((7 + 5)^{8-4})))} := \frac{(9 + ((6 - 1) \times 2))}{(((30 \times 7) - 58) \times 4)} \\
 & := \frac{(9 + (6 - (1 \times 2)))}{(3 + (0 - (7 - (5 \times 84))))} := \frac{(9 + (6 - (1 + 2)))}{((30 + (7 - 5)) \times (8 + 4))} := \frac{(9 + (6 \times (1 \times 2)))}{((3 - ((0 \times 7) - 5)) \times 84)} \\
 & := \frac{(9 + (6 \times (1 + 2)))}{(3 \times (0 + (75 \times (8 \times 4))))} := \frac{(9 + (6 + (1^2)))}{(((3 \times (0 + 7)) - 5) \times (8 \times 4))} := \frac{(9 + (6 + (1 + 2)))}{(((3 - (0 - 7)) \times 58) - 4)} \\
 & := \frac{(9 + (6 - 12))}{((3 + (0 - (7 \times (5 - 8)))) \times 4)} := \frac{(96 \times 12)}{((3^{07-5}) \times (8^4))} := \frac{(96 \times (1^2))}{(3 \times (0 + (((7 - 5)^8) \times 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{(96 - 12)}{((30 + (7 - 5)) \times 84)}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.28 29 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10654}{37289} & := \frac{(((1^{06}) + 5) \times 4)}{(3 + (7 + (2 + (8 \times 9))))} := \frac{((1^{06}) \times (5 \times 4))}{(3 - (7 - (2 + (8 \times 9))))} := \frac{((1^{06}) + (5 + 4))}{(3 + (7 + ((2 \times 8) + 9)))} \\
 & := \frac{((10 \times (6 + 5)) + 4)}{(3 \times (7 \times (2 + (8 \times 9))))} := \frac{((10 \times (6 + 5)) - 4)}{(372 + (8 - 9))} := \frac{((10 \times 65) - 4)}{((3^7) + (2 + (8 \times 9)))} \\
 & := \frac{((10 + (6 + 5)) \times 4)}{(3 \times (7 + (2 + 89)))} := \frac{((10 + 6) \times 54)}{(3 \times (7 \times (2 \times (8 \times 9))))} := \frac{((10 - 6) \times (5 \times 4))}{((3 - 7) \times (2 - (8 \times 9)))} \\
 & := \frac{((106 + 5) \times 4)}{(3 \times (7 \times (2 + (8 \times 9))))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - ((6 - 5)^4)))}{(3 + (7 - (2 - (8 - 9))))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (6 + (5^4))))}{((3^7) + ((2 \times 8) + 9))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (0 - (6 + (5 + 4))))}{(37 + (2 + (8 + 9)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (6 + (5 - 4))))}{((3 \times (7 + 2)) - (8 - 9))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (65 - 4)))}{((3 \times 72) - (8 - 9))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((6 + 5) \times 4)))}{(3 + (7 + (2 \times (8 \times 9))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (6 \times (5 + 4))))}{(3 \times ((7 + 2) \times 8) - 9)} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (6 \times (5 - 4))))}{(3 \times (7^{2+8-9}))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (6 + (5 \times 4))))}{(37 - ((2 - 8) \times 9))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (6 + 54)))}{(3 + ((7 + (2 \times 8)) \times 9))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (65 \times 4)))}{((3 + 7) \times (2 + 89))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (0 - (6 - (5 + 4))))}{((3 \times (7 - 2)) + (8 - 9))} := \frac{(10 \times ((6 - 5) \times 4))}{(3 - (7 - (2 \times (8 \times 9))))} := \frac{(10 \times (6 - (5 - 4)))}{(((3 \times 7) + 2) \times 8) - 9)} \\
 & := \frac{(10 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))}{(3 \times (7 \times ((2 + 8) \times 9)))} := \frac{(10 \times (6 + (5 + 4)))}{(3 \times (7 \times ((2 \times 8) + 9)))} := \frac{(10 \times (6 + 54))}{((3^7) + (2 - 89))} \\
 & := \frac{(10 + (65 \times 4))}{(3 \times ((7 + 28) \times 9))} := \frac{(106 + (5 \times 4))}{(((3 \times 7) + 28) \times 9)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13854}{69270} & := \frac{(((1 + 3) \times 85) - 4)}{((6 + (9 \times 2)) \times 70)} := \frac{((1^3) \times (8 \times (5 - 4)))}{((6 \times 9) - (2 \times (7 - 0)))} := \frac{((1^3) \times (85 - 4))}{((6 + 9) \times (27 - 0))} \\
 & := \frac{((1^3) + (8 \times (5 - 4)))}{((6 \times 9) - (2 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{((13 + 8) \times (5 \times 4))}{((6 + 9) \times (2 \times 70))} := \frac{(1 - (3 - ((8 \times 5) + 4)))}{((6 + 9) \times (2 \times (7 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (3 - (8 + (5 - 4))))}{((6 \times (9 - 2)) - (7 - 0))} := \frac{(1 - (38 - (5^4)))}{(6 \times ((9 - 2) \times 70))} := \frac{(1 \times ((3^8-5) - 4))}{((6 \times (9 \times 2)) + (7 - 0))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (3 - (8 - (5 + 4))))}{(6 + (9 - (2 - (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 \times (3 \times (8 - (5 - 4))))}{(6 + (92 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 \times (3 \times (8 \times (5 + 4))))}{((6 + 9) \times (2 + 70))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (3 \times (8 + (5 - 4))))}{((6 + 9) \times (2 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 \times (3 + (8 - (5 + 4))))}{(6 + (9 + (2 - (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 \times (3 + (8 \times (5 - 4))))}{(6 + ((9 - 2) \times (7 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (3 + (8 + (5 \times 4))))}{(6 + (9 + (2 \times 70)))} := \frac{(1 \times (3 + (8 + (5 + 4))))}{(((6 + 9) \times 2) + 70)} := \frac{(1 \times (38 - (5 + 4)))}{((69 \times 2) + (7 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + ((3^{8-5}) \times 4))}{((6 \times 92) - (7 - 0))} := \frac{(1 + (3 - (8 - (5 \times 4))))}{(6 + ((9^2) - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + (3 \times (8 \times (5 - 4))))}{(6 - (9 - (2^7 + 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (3 + (8 - (5 + 4))))}{((6 - 9) \times (2 - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + (3 + (8 \times (5 - 4))))}{(69 - (2 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + (3 + (8 + (5 - 4))))}{(6 - (9 + (2 - 70)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (38 - (5 + 4)))}{(6 \times ((9 \times 2) + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + (38 + (5 \times 4)))}{(((6 + 9)^2) + 70)} := \frac{(13 + ((8 \times 5) + 4))}{(6 + (9 + 270))} \\
 &:= \frac{(13 + (85 + 4))}{(6 \times (92 - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(138 - (5 - 4))}{(692 - (7 - 0))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{14538}{72690}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((1 + (4 + 5))^3) + 8)}{(7 \times ((2 + 6) \times 90))} := \frac{(((1 - 4) \times (5 - 3)) + 8)}{(7 + ((2 \times 6) - (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 - (4 - (5 - (3 - 8))))}{(7 \times (2 - (6 - (9 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (4 - (5 + (3 + 8))))}{((7 \times (2 + 6)) + (9 - 0))} := \frac{(1 - (4 - (53 - 8)))}{(7 \times (2 \times (6 + (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 - (4 \times (5 - (3 \times 8))))}{(7 \times ((2^6) - (9 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (4 + (5 - (3 \times 8))))}{(7 + ((2^6) + (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 - (4 + (5 \times (3 - 8))))}{((7 \times 2) + (6 + 90))} := \frac{(1 \times ((4 + (5 + 3)) \times 8))}{((7 - 2) \times (6 + 90))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((4 + 5) \times (3 \times 8)))}{(72 \times (6 + (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 \times ((4 + 5) \times (3 + 8)))}{(((7^2) + 6) \times (9 - 0))} := \frac{(1 \times ((4 + 5) \times 38))}{((7 + (2 \times 6)) \times 90)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 - (5 - (3 \times 8))))}{(7 + (2 \times (6 \times (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 \times (4 - (5 \times (3 - 8))))}{(7 + (2 \times (69 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 \times (4 - (5 + (3 - 8))))}{(7 - (2 - (6 + (9 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 + ((5 \times 3) + 8)))}{((7 + (2 + 6)) \times (9 - 0))} := \frac{(1 \times (4 + (53 - 8)))}{(7 \times (26 + (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + (((4 + 5) \times 3) + 8))}{(((7 \times 2) + 6) \times (9 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + ((4 - (5 - 3)) \times 8))}{(7 - ((2 \times 6) - 90))} := \frac{(1 + ((4^{5-3}) - 8))}{(((7 + 2) \times 6) - (9 - 0))} := \frac{(1 + ((45 \times 3) + 8))}{(((7 \times 2) - 6) \times 90)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (4 - (5 - (3 \times 8))))}{(((7 - 2) \times 6) + 90)} := \frac{(1 + (4 + ((5 + 3) \times 8)))}{((7 - 2) \times (69 - 0))} := \frac{(1 + (4 + (5 - (3 - 8))))}{((7 \times (2 \times 6)) - (9 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (4 + (5 + (3 + 8))))}{(7 + (2 + (6 + 90)))} := \frac{(1 + (45 - (3 + 8)))}{(7 - (2 \times (6 - 90)))} := \frac{(1 + (45 + (3 + 8)))}{(((7^2) \times 6) - (9 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(14 + ((5^3) + 8))}{(726 + (9 - 0))} := \frac{(14 + ((5 - 3)^8))}{((7 + (2 + 6)) \times 90)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{15084}{26397}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((1 + 50) \times 8) + 4)}{(((2^6) + 39) \times 7)} := \frac{((1 - (5 \times (0 - 8))) \times 4)}{(2 - (6 - (3 \times 97)))} := \frac{((1 - (5 + (0 - 8))) \times 4)}{(2 - (6 - (39 - 7)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 - (5 + (0 - 8)))^4)}{((2 \times (6^3)) + (9 + 7))} := \frac{((1^{508}) \times 4)}{(2 + (6 - (3 - (9 - 7))))} := \frac{((1^5 + 0) \times (8 \times 4))}{(2 + (6 \times (3^{9-7})))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1^5 + 0) \times (8 + 4))}{(2 + (6 - (3 - (9 + 7))))} := \frac{((1 + (5 - (0 \times 8))) \times 4)}{(2 - (6 - (39 + 7)))} := \frac{((1 + (5 - (0 \times 8)))^4)}{(2 \times (6 \times (3 \times (9 \times 7))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (5 - (0 - 8))) \times 4)}{((2 + (6 - (3 - 9))) \times 7)} := \frac{((1 + (5 - 0)) \times (8 + 4))}{(2 \times (((6 \times 3) - 9) \times 7))} := \frac{((1 + 50) \times (8 - 4))}{(((2 \times 6) + 39) \times 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{((15 - (0 - 8)) \times 4)}{((2 - (6 - (3 \times 9))) \times 7)} := \frac{((1 - 5) \times (0 - (8 \times 4)))}{((26 - (3 - 9)) \times 7)} := \frac{((1 - 5) \times (0 - (8 + 4)))}{((2^6) + ((3 \times 9) - 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{((15 \times (0 + 8)) - 4)}{(2 + ((6 - 3) \times 9)) \times 7} := \frac{(1 - (5 + (0 - (8 \times 4))))}{(2 + (63 - (9 + 7)))} := \frac{(1 - (5 + (0 - (8 + 4))))}{(2 \times (6 + (3 - (9 - 7))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(1 - (5 + (0 - 84)))}{((2 + (6 + (3 + 9))) \times 7)} := \frac{(1 \times ((5 \times (0 + 8)) + 4))}{((2 + ((6 \times 3) - 9)) \times 7)} := \frac{(1 \times ((5 \times (0 + 8)) - 4))}{(2 + (63 - (9 - 7)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((50 \times 8) - 4))}{((2 + (6 + 3)) \times (9 \times 7))} := \frac{(1 \times ((50 + 8) \times 4))}{(((2^6) + (3 - 9)) \times 7)} := \frac{(1 \times (5 \times (0 + (8 + 4))))}{((2^{6-3}) + 97)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (5 \times (0 + (8 - 4))))}{(26 + (3^{9-7}))} := \frac{(15 \times (0 + (8 + 4)))}{(2 + ((6^3) + 97))} := \frac{(150 \times (8 + 4))}{(2 \times (((6^3) + 9) \times 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{1508 + 4}{2639 + 7} := \frac{1508 - 4}{2639 - 7}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{15846}{79230} =$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((1 - (5 - 8))^4) \times 6)}{(((7 + 9)^2) \times 30)} := \frac{((1^5) \times (8 \times (4 \times 6)))}{((7 + 9) \times (2 \times 30))} := \frac{((1^5) + (84 - 6))}{(79 \times (2 + (3 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (5 \times (8 + 4))) \times 6)}{(((7 \times 9) - 2) \times 30)} := \frac{((1 + (5 + (8 + 4))) \times 6)}{((7 + (9 + 2)) \times 30)} := \frac{((15 \times (8 \times 4)) + 6)}{((79 + 2) \times 30)} \\
 &:= \frac{((15 \times (8 + 4)) + 6)}{(7 + (923 - 0))} := \frac{((15 + 84) \times 6)}{((7 + 92) \times 30)} := \frac{((15 - 8) \times (4 + 6))}{(7 + ((9 - 2)^3 + 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 - 58) \times (4 - 6))}{((7 \times (9^2)) + (3 - 0))} := \frac{(1 - (((5 - 8) \times 4) - 6))}{((7 \times 9) + (2 + 30))} := \frac{(1 - (5 - (8 - (4 - 6))))}{(7 - (9 - (2 + 30)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (5 - (8 + (4 + 6))))}{(7 \times (9 - (2 - (3 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 - (5 - (8 + (4 - 6))))}{(7 + (9 - (2 \times (3 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 - (5 - (8 + 46)))}{(7 + ((9^2) \times (3 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (5 - (8 - (4 + 6))))}{(((7 + 9) \times 2) + (3 - 0))} := \frac{(1 \times (5 - (8 \times (4 - 6))))}{(7 \times (9 + (2 \times (3 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 \times (5 \times (84 - 6)))}{(((7 \times 9) + 2) \times 30)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (5 + (8 - (4 + 6))))}{(7 + (9 + (2 - (3 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 \times (5 + (8 - (4 - 6))))}{((7 + (9 \times 2)) \times (3 - 0))} := \frac{(1 \times (5 + (8 + (4 - 6))))}{(7 + ((9 \times 2) + 30))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (5 + (8 + 46)))}{(7 + (9 \times (2 + 30)))} := \frac{(1 + ((5 \times 8) - (4 \times 6)))}{(7 + ((9^2) - (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + ((5 \times 8) + (4 - 6)))}{(((7 \times 9) + 2) \times (3 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (5 - (8 - (4 + 6))))}{(7 + ((9 + 2) \times (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + (5 \times (8 + (4 - 6))))}{((79 \times 2) - (3 - 0))} := \frac{(1 + (5 + (8 - (4 - 6))))}{((7 \times (9 + 2)) + (3 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (5 + (84 - 6)))}{((7 + (9 - 2)) \times 30)} := \frac{(15 \times (8 - (4 - 6)))}{((7 + (9 \times 2)) \times 30)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{18074}{63259} =$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((1^8 + 0) \times (7 \times 4))}{((6 + (3 - 2)) \times (5 + 9))} := \frac{((1^8 + 0) \times 74)}{((6^3) - (2 - (5 \times 9)))} := \frac{((1 + (8 - (0 - 7))) \times 4)}{((6^3) - (2 \times (5 - 9)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (8 + (0 - 7)))^4)}{(6 + (3 + (2 + (5 \times 9))))} := \frac{((1 + (8 - 0)) \times 74)}{((6 + 3) \times 259)} := \frac{((18 + (0 - 7)) \times 4)}{((6 + (3 + 2)) \times (5 + 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (8 + (0 - (7 + 4))))}{(6 - (((3 - 2)^5) - 9))} := \frac{(1 \times ((8 - (0 - 7)) \times 4))}{((6 + (3^2)) \times (5 + 9))} := \frac{(1 \times ((8 \times (0 + 7)) - 4))}{((6^3) - (25 + 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 - (0 - (7 \times 4))))}{(6 \times ((3 \times (2 \times 5)) - 9))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 - (0 \times 74)))}{(6 + (3 + ((2 \times 5) + 9)))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 \times ((0 \times 7) + 4)))}{((63 \times 2) - (5 + 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (0 + (7 - 4))))}{(((6 + (3^2)) \times 5) + 9)} := \frac{(1 \times (80 + (7 \times 4)))}{(63 \times (2 - (5 - 9)))} := \frac{(1 + ((8 + (0 - 7))^4))}{(6 + (3 + (2 + (5 - 9))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (8 - (0 - (7 + 4))))}{(6 + (3 + (2 + 59)))} := \frac{(1 + (8 - (0 - (7 - 4))))}{(6 - (3 \times (2 - (5 + 9))))} := \frac{(1 + (8 + (0 - (7 - 4))))}{(6 + (3 - (2 - (5 + 9))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (80 - (7 - 4)))}{((6^3) - (2 - 59))} := \frac{(1 + (80 + (7 + 4)))}{(6 + (325 - 9))} := \frac{(18 - ((0 \times 7) - 4))}{(((6 + 3)^2) + (5 - 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{(18 - (0 \times 74))}{(6 + (3 \times ((2 \times 5) + 9)))} := \frac{(18 \times ((0 \times 7) + 4))}{((6 - (3 - 25)) \times 9)} := \frac{(18 \times (0 + (7 \times 4)))}{(63 \times (2 \times (5 + 9)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(18 \times (0 + (7^4)))}{(((6 + (3 - 2))^5) \times 9)} := \frac{(18 \times (0 + (7 - 4)))}{(6 + (3 \times (2 + 59)))} := \frac{(18 \times (0 + 74))}{(6 \times (3 \times 259))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(180 - (7 \times 4))}{((6 + 32) \times (5 + 9))} \quad := \frac{(180 \times (7 - 4))}{(6 \times ((3 + (2^5)) \times 9))}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{18476}{23095} &:= \frac{(((1^8) + 47) \times 6)}{((2^3 + 0) \times (9 \times 5))} &:= \frac{(((18 + 4) \times 7) - 6)}{(230 - (9 \times 5))} &:= \frac{(((18 - 4) \times 7) - 6)}{((2 + (30 - 9)) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{((1^{84}) \times 76)}{((2 - 3) \times (0 - 95))} &:= \frac{((1 + (8 + (4 + 7))) \times 6)}{(2 \times (30 + (9 \times 5)))} &:= \frac{((1 + (8 + (4 - 7))) \times 6)}{((2 - 3) \times (0 - (9 \times 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + (8 - 4)) \times 76)}{((2 + (3 - 0)) \times 95)} &:= \frac{((18 \times (4 + 7)) + 6)}{(((2 \times 30) - 9) \times 5)} &:= \frac{((18 \times (4 + 7)) - 6)}{(2 \times (30 \times (9 - 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{((18 + (4 \times 7)) \times 6)}{(((2 \times 30) + 9) \times 5)} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((8 \times 4) + 76))}{(230 - 95)} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((8 + (4 \times 7)) \times 6))}{(2 \times (3 \times (0 + (9 \times 5))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times ((8 - 4) \times (7 \times 6)))}{(2 \times ((30 - 9) \times 5))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 - (4 \times (7 - 6))))}{(2 + (3 - (0 \times 95)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 - (4 - 76)))}{(2 + (3 - (0 - 95)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (4 - (7 - 6))))}{(2 \times (3 \times ((0 \times 9) + 5)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (4 \times 76)))}{((2 + 30) \times 95)} &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (4 \times (7 - 6))))}{((2 - (3 + (0 - 9))) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (4 + (7 - 6))))}{(2 + (3 - (0 - (9 \times 5))))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (47 + 6)))}{(2 \times ((30 \times 9) - 5))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 + (4 \times (7 + 6))))}{(((2 \times (3 - 0)) + 9) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 + (4 \times 76)))}{(2 \times ((30 + 9) \times 5))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 + (4 \times (7 - 6))))}{((2 \times 30) - (9 \times 5))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (84 \times (7 - 6)))}{((2 \times 30) + (9 \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (84 - 76))}{(2 + (3 - ((0 \times 9) - 5)))} &:= \frac{(1 + ((8 \times 4) - (7 + 6)))}{((2 + (3 - (0 \times 9))) \times 5)} &:= \frac{(18 - (4 - (7 \times 6)))}{((2 + (3 - (0 - 9))) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(18 \times (4 + (7 \times 6)))}{(23 \times (0 + (9 \times 5)))} &:= \frac{(184 + 76)}{(230 + 95)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{50463}{89712} &:= \frac{(((50 - 4) \times 6) + 3)}{(8 \times ((9 \times 7) - (1^2)))} &:= \frac{((5 - (0 - (4 + 6))) \times 3)}{(8 + (9 \times (7 + (1^2))))} &:= \frac{((5 - (0 - (4 - 6))) \times 3)}{(8 \times (9 - (7 \times (1^2))))} \\ &:= \frac{((5 - (0 - 4)) \times (6 \times 3))}{(8 \times (9 \times (7 - (1 + 2))))} &:= \frac{((5 - (0 - 4)) \times (6 + 3))}{(8 \times (9 + (7 + (1 \times 2))))} &:= \frac{((5 - (0 - 4)) \times 63)}{(8 \times (9 \times (7 \times (1 \times 2))))} \\ &:= \frac{((5 - (0 - 4))^{6+3})}{(8 \times ((9^{7+1}) \times 2))} &:= \frac{((5 - (0 - 46)) \times 3)}{(8 \times ((9 + (7 + 1)) \times 2))} &:= \frac{((5 \times (0 + (4 \times 6))) - 3)}{((8 + (97 - 1)) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{((5 + (0 - 4)) \times (6^3))}{(8 \times ((9 + 7) \times (1 + 2)))} &:= \frac{((5 + (0 - 4)) \times 63)}{(8 \times (9 - (7 - 12)))} &:= \frac{((50 + (4 - 6)) \times 3)}{((8 \times (9 - (7 \times 1)))^2)} \\ &:= \frac{((50 + 4) \times 63)}{(8 \times (9 \times (7 \times 12)))} &:= \frac{((50 + 46) \times 3)}{(8^{9-7+12})} &:= \frac{(5 - (0 - (4 + (6 \times 3))))}{(8 - (9 - (7 \times (1 \times 2))))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 - (0 - (4 + (6 + 3))))}{(8 \times (9 + (7 - 12)))} &:= \frac{(5 - (0 - (4 + 63)))}{(8 \times (9 + (7 \times (1^2))))} &:= \frac{(5 - (0 - (46 + 3)))}{(89 + (7 \times (1^2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 \times ((0 \times 4) + (6 \times 3)))}{((8 + (9 \times (7 + 1))) \times 2)} &:= \frac{(5 \times ((0 \times 4) + 63))}{(8 \times ((9 \times (7 + 1)) - 2))} &:= \frac{(5 \times (0 + ((4 \times 6) + 3)))}{(8 \times (9 + (7 \times (1 + 2))))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 \times (0 + (4 \times (6 + 3))))}{((89 + 71) \times 2)} &:= \frac{(50 \times (4 \times (6 \times 3)))}{((8 + (9 \times (7 + 1)))^2)} &:= \frac{(50 + (4 - (6 \times 3)))}{(8^{9-7 \times 1^2})} \\ &:= \frac{(50 + (4 + (6^3)))}{(8 \times ((9 \times 7) - (1 + 2)))} &:= \frac{(50 + (46 + 3))}{((8 + (9 + 71)) \times 2)} &:= \frac{(504 - (6 \times 3))}{(8 \times (9 \times ((7 - 1) \times 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(504 + (6^3))}{(8 \times ((9 + 71) \times 2))} &:= \frac{(504 - 63)}{(8 \times (97 + (1^2)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{59368}{74210} := \frac{(((5 \times 9) + (3 \times 6)) \times 8)}{((7 - 4) \times 210)} \quad := \frac{(((5 \times 9) + (3 - 6)) \times 8)}{(7 \times ((4 + 2) \times 10))} \quad := \frac{(((5 \times 9) - 36) \times 8)}{((7 + (4 - 2)) \times 10)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((5+9)^3) \times (6+8))}{((7^4) \times (2 \times 10))} := \frac{((5-(9-(3 \times 6))) \times 8)}{(7 \times ((4-2) \times 10))} := \frac{((5 \times (9+3)) - (6 \times 8))}{(7 - (4 - (2+10)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 \times (9-3)) - (6+8))}{((7 \times 4) + (2-10))} := \frac{((5 \times (9-3)) - (6-8))}{((7 \times 4) + (2+10))} := \frac{((5 \times (9-3)) + (6+8))}{(7 + (4 \times (2+10)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 \times (9-3)) + (6-8))}{(7 \times (4 + (2 - (1-0))))} := \frac{((5 + ((9 \times 3) - 6)) \times 8)}{(((7 \times 4) - 2) \times 10)} := \frac{((5 + (9 \times 3)) \times (6+8))}{(7 \times (4 \times (2 \times 10)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 + (9 + (3+6))) \times 8)}{((7 + (4^2)) \times 10)} := \frac{((5+9) \times (36-8))}{((7+42) \times 10)} := \frac{((5+93) \times (6 \times 8))}{(7 \times (4 \times 210))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5-93) \times (6-8))}{((7+4) \times (2 \times 10))} := \frac{(5 - (9 - (3 \times (6 \times 8))))}{(7 \times (4 + (21-0)))} := \frac{(5 - (9 - (36-8)))}{((7 \times 4) + (2 \times (1-0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 - (9 \times (3 - (6+8))))}{((7 + (4+2)) \times 10)} := \frac{(5 \times ((9 + (3-6)) \times 8))}{(((7 \times 4) + 2) \times 10)} := \frac{(5 \times (9 - (3 - (6-8))))}{(7 + ((4 \times 2) + 10))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times (9 - (3 + (6-8))))}{(5 \times (9 - (3 + (6-8))))} := \frac{(5 + (9 - ((3 \times 6) - 8)))}{(5 + (9 - ((3 \times 6) - 8)))} := \frac{(5 + (9 + (3 \times (6-8))))}{(5 + (9 + (3 \times (6-8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (42 + (1-0)))}{(5 + (93 - (6+8)))} := \frac{(7 - (4 - (2 \times (1-0))))}{(5 + (93 + (6-8)))} := \frac{(7 + (4 - (2 - (1-0))))}{(59 + (3 - (6+8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (93 - (6+8)))}{(7 \times ((4^2) - (1-0)))} := \frac{(5 + (93 + (6-8)))}{(((7+4)^2) - (1-0))} := \frac{(59 + (3 - (6+8)))}{((7-4) \times (2 \times 10))} \\
 &:= \frac{(59 + (3 + (6+8)))}{(74 + (21-0))} := \frac{(59 + (3 + (6-8)))}{(74 + (2 - (1-0)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{73460}{91825}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((7-3) \times 4)^6 + 0)}{((9+1) \times (8^{2+5}))} := \frac{(((7-3) \times 4) + 60)}{(9 - (1 - (82+5)))} := \frac{(((7-3)^4) + 60)}{(((9 \times (1+8)) - 2) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 - (3-4)) \times (6-0))}{(9 + (1 + ((8+2) \times 5)))} := \frac{((7 \times (3 \times 4)) + 60)}{((9 + (1+8)) \times (2 \times 5))} := \frac{((7 \times (3 \times 4)) - 60)}{(9 + (1 \times ((8 \times 2) + 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 + (3^4)) \times 60)}{((9-1) \times 825)} := \frac{((7 + (3+4)) \times (6-0))}{(((9 + (1^8))^2) + 5)} := \frac{((7 + (3-4)) \times (6-0))}{(9 \times (1 \times (8 + (2-5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 + (3-4)) \times 60)}{((9 - (1-82)) \times 5)} := \frac{((7+3) \times (4 \times (6-0)))}{((9+1) \times ((8-2) \times 5))} := \frac{((7+3) \times (4 + (6-0)))}{((9 + (1 \times (8 \times 2))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7+3) \times (4+60))}{(((9 \times 18) - 2) \times 5)} := \frac{((7-3) \times (4 \times (6-0)))}{((9 - (1 - (8 \times 2))) \times 5)} := \frac{((7-3) \times (4^6 + 0))}{(((9-1) \times 8)^2 \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7-3) \times (4 + (6-0)))}{(9 + (1 + (8 + (2^5))))} := \frac{(((9 - (1^8))^2) \times 5)}{((7-3) \times (4+60))} := \frac{(7 - (3 - (4 \times (6-0))))}{(9 + ((1^8) + 25))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 - (3 - (4+60)))}{(9 - (1 - (82-5)))} := \frac{(7 - (3 + (4-60)))}{((9 + (1 \times (8-2))) \times 5)} := \frac{(7 - (3 - 460))}{((9 \times (1 + (8^2))) - 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 \times (3 \times (4 \times (6-0))))}{(9 \times (1 + ((8^2) + 5)))} := \frac{(7 \times (34 + (6-0)))}{(((9 \times (1 \times 8)) - 2) \times 5)} := \frac{(7 + ((3^4) + 60))}{(9 \times (18 + 2)) + 5} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (3 - (4 - (6-0))))}{(9 + (1 + (8 + (2-5))))} := \frac{(7 + (3 + (4 - (6-0))))}{(9 + (1^{825}))} := \frac{(7 + (3 + (4 + (6-0))))}{(9 - (1 + (8-25)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (3 + (46-0)))}{(9 - (1 - (8-2))) \times 5} := \frac{(734 + (6-0))}{(918 + (2+5))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{74816}{93520}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((7 \times 4) + (8 \times 1)) \times 6)}{(9 \times (3 \times (5 \times (2-0))))} := \frac{((7 - (4 - (8+1))) \times 6)}{(9 \times (3 + (5 + (2-0))))} := \frac{((7 - (4-8)) \times 16)}{((9 - (3-5)) \times 20)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 - (4-81)) \times 6)}{(9 \times (35 \times (2-0)))} := \frac{((7 \times 48) + 16)}{(((9 \times 3) - 5) \times 20)} := \frac{((7 + ((4 \times 8) + 1)) \times 6)}{((9+3) \times (5+20))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((7 + (4 - (8+1)))^6)}{(((9+3) \times 5) + 20)} := \frac{(((7 + (4 + (8+1))) \times 6)}{((9-3) \times (5+20))} := \frac{(((7 + (4 + (8-1))) \times 6)}{(9 \times (35-20))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7+4) \times (8 \times 16))}{((93-5) \times 20)} := \frac{((74 - (8 \times 1)) \times 6)}{(9 \times (3 + (52-0)))} := \frac{((7-4) \times (8 \times 16))}{((9 + (3 \times 5)) \times 20)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(74 \times (8-1)) - 6}{((9 \times 3) + 5) \times 20} := \frac{(7 - (4 - (8 - (1 - 6))))}{((9 - (3 + 5)) \times 20)} := \frac{(7 - (4 - (8 + (1^6))))}{(9 + (3 + (5 - (2 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 \times (4 \times (8 - (1 \times 6))))}{(9 \times (3 + 5)) - (2 - 0)} := \frac{(7 \times (4 \times (8 \times (1 + 6))))}{((93 + 5) \times 20)} := \frac{(7 \times (4 \times (8 + (1^6))))}{(9 \times ((3 \times 5) + 20))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 \times (4^{8-1 \times 6}))}{(9 + (3 - 5)) \times 20} := \frac{(7 + ((4 \times 8) - (1 + 6)))}{(((9 + 3) \times 5) - 20)} := \frac{(7 + ((4 \times 8) + (1^6)))}{(((9 - 3) \times 5) + 20)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (4 - (8 - (1^6))))}{(9 + (3 - (5 + (2 - 0))))} := \frac{(7 + (4 - (8 + (1 - 6))))}{(((9 - 3) \times 5) - 20)} := \frac{(7 + (4 + (8 - (1 - 6))))}{(9 + (3 \times (5 + (2 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (4 + (8 + (1^6))))}{(9 + ((3 + 5) \times (2 - 0)))} := \frac{(7 + (48 - (1 + 6)))}{((9 - 3) \times (5 \times (2 - 0)))} := \frac{(74 + ((8 - 1) \times 6))}{(93 + (52 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{748 + 16}{935 + 20} := \frac{748 - 16}{935 - 20}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{2769}{138450}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((2 \times 7) - 6) \times 9)}{((1^3) \times (8 \times 450))} := \frac{(((2 + 7) \times 6) - 9)}{((1 + ((3 + 8) \times 4)) \times 50)} := \frac{((2 - (7 - 6)) \times 9)}{((13 - (8 - 4)) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (7 + 6)) + 9)}{(1 \times ((3 + (8 \times 4)) \times 50))} := \frac{((2 \times (7 + 6)) - 9)}{((13 + (8 - 4)) \times 50)} := \frac{((2 \times 7) + (6 + 9))}{((1 + ((3 \times 8) + 4)) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times 7) + 69)}{(1 + (3 + ((8^4) + 50)))} := \frac{((2 + (7 - 6)) \times 9)}{((1 + (3 \times 8)) \times (4 + 50))} := \frac{((2 - 7) \times (6 - 9))}{(1 \times ((3 + (8 + 4)) \times 50))} \\
 &:= \frac{((27 \times 6) - 9)}{((1 + (38 \times 4)) \times 50)} := \frac{((27 - 6) \times 9)}{((13 + 8) \times 450)} := \frac{(2 - ((7 - 6)^9))}{(1 + (3 - (8 - (4 + 50))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (7 - (6 + 9)))}{((1 - (3 - (8 + 4))) \times 50)} := \frac{(2 \times (7 - (6 - 9)))}{(1 \times (((3 \times 8) - 4) \times 50))} := \frac{(2 \times (7 + (6 + 9)))}{(1 \times ((3 + 8) \times (4 \times 50)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (7 + (6 - 9)))}{((1 + (3 + (8 - 4))) \times 50)} := \frac{(2 \times (7 + 69))}{(1 \times (38 \times (4 \times 50)))} := \frac{(2 \times (76 - 9))}{((138 - 4) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2^{(7-6) \times 9})}{((1 + (3 \times 8)) \times (4^5 + 0))} := \frac{(2^{(7-6)^9})}{((1 - (3 - (8 - 4))) \times 50)} := \frac{(2^{7+6-9})}{((1 + (3 + (8 + 4))) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + ((7 - 6)^9))}{((1 - (3 - (8 \times 4))) \times (5 - 0))} := \frac{(2 + (7 - (6 - 9)))}{(1 \times (3 \times ((8 - 4) \times 50)))} := \frac{(2 + (7 + (6 + 9)))}{((1 - (3 - 8)) \times (4 \times 50))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (76 + 9))}{(1 \times ((3 + 84) \times 50))} := \frac{(27 - (6 - 9))}{((1 - (3 - (8 \times 4))) \times 50)} := \frac{(27 + (6 \times 9))}{(1 + (3 + ((8^4) - 50)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(27 + (6 + 9))}{(1 \times ((38 + 4) \times 50))} := \frac{(27 + 69)}{(1 \times (3 \times (8 \times (4 \times 50))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{5394}{172608}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((5 \times 3) - 9) \times 4)}{((1 + 7) \times (2 \times (6 \times (0 + 8))))} := \frac{(((5 - 3) \times 9)^4)}{((1^7) \times (2 \times (6^{08})))} := \frac{(((5 - 3) \times 9) - 4)}{(1 \times (7 \times (2^{6+0 \times 8})))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((5 - 3)^9) \times 4)}{((1 + (7 + (2 - (6 - 0))))^8)} := \frac{((5 \times (3 + 9)) + 4)}{((17 \times (2 \times 60)) + 8)} := \frac{((5 \times 3) - (9 + 4))}{(1 - (7 - (2 + (60 + 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 \times 3) + (9 \times 4))}{(17 \times (2 \times (6 \times (0 + 8))))} := \frac{((5^3) - (9 + 4))}{(1 \times (7 \times ((2^6 + 0) \times 8)))} := \frac{((5^3) - 94)}{(((1 + 7)^2) + 60) \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 + (3 \times 9)) \times 4)}{((1 + 7)^{2-6+08})} := \frac{((5 + (3 + 9)) \times 4)}{(17 \times ((2 \times 60) + 8))} := \frac{((5 + 3) \times (9^4))}{((1 - (7 - (2 \times (6 - 0))))^8)} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 + 3) \times (9 + 4))}{(((1 + 7)^2) \times (60 - 8))} := \frac{((5 - 3) \times (9 \times 4))}{((1 - (7^2)) \times (6 \times (0 - 8)))} := \frac{((5 - 3) \times (9 + 4))}{(1 \times ((7 \times (2 \times 60)) - 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 - 3) \times (9 - 4))}{(((17 \times 2) + (6 - 0)) \times 8)} := \frac{((5 - 3)^{9-4})}{((1 + (7 + (2 \times 60))) \times 8)} := \frac{(5 - (3 - (9 \times 4)))}{((1^7) \times (2 \times 608))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(5 - (3 - (9 + 4)))}{((17^2) \times (60 \times 8))} & := \frac{(5 - (3 - (9 - 4)))}{(1 \times (7 \times ((2 - 6) \times (0 - 8))))} & := \frac{(5 - (3 - 94))}{((1 - 7) \times ((2^6) \times (0 - 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{(5 \times ((3 + 9) \times 4))}{((1 + 7) \times (2 \times (60 \times 8)))} & := \frac{(5 \times (3 \times (9 - 4)))}{((1 + (7^2)) \times (6 \times (0 + 8)))} & := \frac{(5 + ((3 \times 9) - 4))}{(1 \times (7 \times ((2 \times 60) + 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{(5 + (3 - (9 - 4)))}{((1 + (7 - (2 - (6 - 0)))) \times 8)} & := \frac{(5 + (3 + (9 + 4)))}{(1 \times (7 \times (2 \times (6 \times (0 + 8)))))} & := \frac{(5 + (3 + (9 - 4)))}{((1 - (7 + (2 - 60))) \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{(53 - (9 \times 4))}{(17 \times ((2 - 6) \times (0 - 8)))} & := \frac{(53 + (9 - 4))}{((172 + 60) \times 8)}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.29 30 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13698}{20547} & := \frac{(((1^3) + (6 \times 9)) \times 8)}{(20 \times (5 + (4 \times 7)))} & := \frac{((1^{36}) \times 98)}{((20 + (5 - 4)) \times 7)} & := \frac{((1^3) - (6 - (9 + 8)))}{(2 - (0 - (5 + (4 + 7))))} \\
 & := \frac{((1^3) + (69 - 8))}{(((20 + 5) \times 4) - 7)} & := \frac{((1 + (3 - (6 - 9))) \times 8)}{(2 \times (0 - (5 - 47)))} & := \frac{((13 - 6) \times (9 \times 8))}{(2 \times (0 + (54 \times 7)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - ((3 \times (6 - 9)) + 8))}{(2 - (0 - ((5 - 4)^7)))} & := \frac{(1 - (3 - ((6 \times 9) - 8)))}{(2 \times (0 + (5 + (4 \times 7))))} & := \frac{(1 - (3 - ((6 + 9) \times 8)))}{(205 - (4 \times 7))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (3 - (6 \times (9 - 8))))}{(2 \times ((0 \times 5) - (4 - 7)))} & := \frac{(1 - (3 + (6 - 98)))}{(((2^{05}) \times 4) + 7)} & := \frac{(1 \times ((3 - (6 - 9)) \times 8))}{(20 + (5 + 47))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times ((3 \times (6 \times 9)) + 8))}{(20 + (5 \times 47))} & := \frac{(1 \times ((3 + (6 + 9)) \times 8))}{(205 + (4 + 7))} & := \frac{(1 \times (3 - (6 - (9 + 8))))}{((2 - (0 - (5 - 4))) \times 7)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (3 \times ((6 + 9) \times 8)))}{(20 \times ((5 \times 4) + 7))} & := \frac{(1 \times (3 \times (6 \times (9 - 8))))}{(20 + ((5 - 4) \times 7))} & := \frac{(1 \times (3 + (6 - (9 - 8))))}{(2 \times (0 - (5 - (4 + 7))))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (36 \times (9 - 8)))}{(2 - (0 - (5 + 47)))} & := \frac{(1 + (((3 + 6) \times 9) - 8))}{((20 \times 5) + (4 + 7))} & := \frac{(1 + ((3 \times (6 + 9)) + 8))}{(20 + (54 + 7))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + ((3 \times (6 + 9)) - 8))}{(2 - (0 - (5 \times (4 + 7))))} & := \frac{(1 + (3 - ((6 - 9) \times 8)))}{(((2 \times (0 + 5)) - 4) \times 7)} & := \frac{(1 + (3 \times (6 + (9 - 8))))}{((2 \times (0 + (5 \times 4))) - 7)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (3 + ((6 \times 9) - 8)))}{(20 + (5 \times (4 + 7)))} & := \frac{(1 + (3 + (6 \times (9 - 8))))}{(2 - (0 - ((5 \times 4) - 7)))} & := \frac{(1 + (36 - (9 + 8)))}{(2 \times (0 - (5 \times (4 - 7))))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (369 + 8))}{(20 + 547)} & := \frac{(13 - (6 - (9 + 8)))}{(20 + (5 + (4 + 7)))} & := \frac{(13 - (6 + (9 - 8)))}{(2 - ((0 \times 54) - 7))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{21564}{97038} & := \frac{(((2 + (1^5))^6) \times 4)}{((9 - (7 - 0)) \times (3^8))} & := \frac{((2 - (1^5)) \times (6 \times 4))}{(9 \times (7 + (0 - (3 - 8))))} & := \frac{((2 \times (1 + 56)) + 4)}{(9 \times (70 - (3 + 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{((2 + (15 + 6)) \times 4)}{(9 \times (70 - (3 \times 8)))} & := \frac{((2 + 1) \times (5 \times (6 + 4)))}{(9 \times (70 - (3 - 8)))} & := \frac{((2 - 1) \times (56 \times 4))}{(970 + 38)} \\
 & := \frac{((21 - 5) \times (6 + 4))}{(9 \times ((7 - (0 - 3)) \times 8))} & := \frac{(2 - (1 - (5 - (6 - 4))))}{(9 \times (7 - (0 - (3 - 8))))} & := \frac{(2 - (1 - (5^{6-4})))}{(9 \times ((7 \times (0 + 3)) - 8))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 - (1 - (5 + 64)))}{(9 \times (7 \times (0 - (3 - 8))))} & := \frac{(2 \times (((1 + 5) \times 6) + 4))}{(9 + ((7^{03}) + 8))} & := \frac{(2 \times (((1 + 5)^6) \times 4))}{(((9 - (7 - 0)) \times 3)^8)} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times ((1^5) + 64))}{(9 \times (70 + (3 - 8)))} & := \frac{(2 \times ((15 \times 6) + 4))}{(9 \times (70 + (3 \times 8)))} & := \frac{(2 \times (1 \times (5 \times (6 - 4))))}{(9 + (70 + (3 + 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times (1 \times (5 + (6 \times 4))))}{(9 \times ((7 \times (0 + 3)) + 8))} & := \frac{(2 \times (1 \times (5 + (6 + 4))))}{(9 \times (7 - ((0 \times 3) - 8)))} & := \frac{(2 \times (1 \times (5 + (6 - 4))))}{(9 \times (7 - (0 \times 38)))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times (1 + ((5 + 6) \times 4))}{(9 \times (7 - (0 - 38)))} & := \frac{(2 \times (1 - (5 - (6 + 4))))}{(9 \times ((7 + (0 - 3)) \times 8))} & := \frac{(2 \times (1^{564}))}{(9 - (7 \times (0 \times 38)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(2 \times (1 + (5 - (6 - 4))))}{(9 \times ((7 \times (0 \times 3)) + 8))} := \frac{(2 + (1 - (5 - 64)))}{(9 \times (7 - (0 - (3 \times 8))))} := \frac{(2 + (1 \times ((5 \times 6) + 4)))}{(9 \times (7 - (0 - (3 + 8))))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (1 \times (5 \times (6 - 4))))}{(9 + (7 - (0 - 38)))} := \frac{(2 + (1 + (5 - (6 - 4))))}{(9 + (7 - (0 - (3 + 8))))} := \frac{(2 + (1 + (5 + (6 + 4))))}{(9^{7+03-8})} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + (156 + 4))}{(9 \times (70 + (3 + 8)))} := \frac{(2 + (156 - 4))}{(9 \times (7 \times (0 + (3 + 8))))} := \frac{2 + 1564}{9 + 7038} \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{36728}{45910}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(((3 - (6 - 7))^2) \times 8)}{(4 \times (5 \times (9 - (1 - 0))))} := \frac{(((3 \times 6) - (7 + 2)) \times 8)}{(4 - (5 - (91 - 0)))} := \frac{(((3 + 6)^{7+2}) \times 8)}{(((4 + 5)^9) \times 10)} \\ &:= \frac{((3 - ((6 - 7) \times 2)) \times 8)}{(4 + ((5 \times 9) + (1 - 0)))} := \frac{((3 - (6 - (7 \times 2))) \times 8)}{((4 \times 5) + (9 \times 10))} := \frac{((3 - (6 - (7^2))) \times 8)}{(459 + (1 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{((3 - (6 - (7 + 2))) \times 8)}{(4 \times (5 + (9 + (1 - 0))))} := \frac{((3 \times (6 \times 7)) + (2 + 8))}{((4 \times (5 \times 9)) - 10)} := \frac{((3 + ((6 + 7) \times 2)) \times 8)}{(((4 \times 5) + 9) \times 10)} \\ &:= \frac{((3 + (6 + (7 - 2))) \times 8)}{(4 \times ((5 \times 9) - 10))} := \frac{((3 + (6 + 7)) \times (2 + 8))}{(4 \times (5 \times (9 + (1 - 0))))} := \frac{((3 + (6 + 7)) \times 28)}{(4 \times ((5 + 9) \times 10))} \\ &:= \frac{((3 + (6 + 72)) \times 8)}{((4 + 5) \times (9 \times 10))} := \frac{((3 + 6) \times 728)}{((4 + 5) \times 910)} := \frac{((36 - (7 \times 2)) \times 8)}{(4 \times ((5 \times 9) + 10))} \\ &:= \frac{((36 \times (7 + 2)) + 8)}{((45 \times 9) + 10)} := \frac{((36 \times (7 + 2)) - 8)}{((45 \times 9) - 10)} := \frac{((36 \times (7 - 2)) + 8)}{((4 \times 59) - (1 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{((36 - 7) \times 28)}{((4^5) - (9 \times (1 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 - (67 - (2^8)))}{(4 \times (59 + (1 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 \times ((6 - (7 - 2)) \times 8))}{((4 \times 5) + (9 + (1 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times ((6 + (7 + 2)) \times 8))}{(45 \times (9 + (1 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times (5 \times (9 \times (1 - 0))))}{(3 \times (6 - (7 \times (2 - 8))))} := \frac{(45 + (9 \times 10))}{(3 \times (6 \times ((7 \times 2) - 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 \times (6 \times (72 + 8)))}{(4 \times (5 \times (9 \times 10)))} := \frac{(3 + (6 - (7 + (2 - 8))))}{(4 + (5 - (9 - 10)))} := \frac{(3 + (6 + (7 + 28)))}{((4 \times (5 + 9)) - (1 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{(3 + (67 + (2 + 8)))}{(4 + (5 + (91 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 + (67 + (2 - 8)))}{((4 - (5 - 9)) \times 10)} := \frac{36 + 728}{45 + 910} \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{41508}{72639}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{((4 \times (1 \times (5 - 0))) + 8)}{(7^{2-6-3+9})} := \frac{((4 \times (1 \times 50)) + 8)}{(7 \times ((2^6) - (3 + 9)))} := \frac{((4 \times (1 + 50)) + 8)}{(7 \times (26 + (3 \times 9)))} \\ &:= \frac{((4 \times (15 - 0)) + 8)}{(7 \times ((2^6-3) + 9))} := \frac{((4 \times (1 \times (5 - 0))) - 8)}{(7 \times (263 - 9))} := \frac{((4 + (1 \times (5 - 0))) \times 8)}{((7 - (2 - (6 + 3))) \times 9)} \\ &:= \frac{((4 + (1 \times 50)) \times 8)}{(7 \times (2 \times (63 - 9)))} := \frac{((4 + (1^5 + 0)) \times 8)}{(7 - ((2 - (6 + 3)) \times 9))} := \frac{((4 + (1 + (5 - 0))) \times 8)}{(7 \times (2 + (6 + (3 + 9))))} \\ &:= \frac{((4 + (15 - 0)) \times 8)}{(7 \times (2 - (6 \times (3 - 9))))} := \frac{((41 - (5 - 0)) \times 8)}{(7 \times ((2^6-3) \times 9))} := \frac{((41 + (5 - 0)) \times 8)}{(7 - (2 - 639))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 - ((1 - 50) \times 8))}{(7 \times ((2 + (6 + 3)) \times 9))} := \frac{(4 - (1 - (5 - (0 - 8))))}{(7 - (((2 - 6) \times 3) - 9))} := \frac{(4 - (1 \times (5 \times (0 - 8))))}{(7 - (2 - (6 \times (3 + 9))))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times ((1^5 + 0) \times 8))}{(7 \times (2 - (6 - (3 + 9))))} := \frac{(4 \times ((1^5 + 0) + 8))}{(7 + (2 + (63 - 9)))} := \frac{(4 \times ((1 - 5) \times (0 - 8)))}{(7 \times (26 - (3 - 9)))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (1 \times (5 - (0 \times 8))))}{((7 \times 2) - (6 - (3 \times 9)))} := \frac{(4 \times (1 \times (50 + 8)))}{(7 \times ((2^6) + (3 - 9)))} := \frac{(4 \times (1 + (5 - (0 \times 8))))}{(7 + (2 - (6 - 39)))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (1 + (5 - (0 - 8))))}{(7 \times (2 + (6 - (3 - 9))))} := \frac{(4 \times (15 - (0 \times 8)))}{(4 \times (15 - (0 \times 8)))} := \frac{(4 \times (15 - (0 - 8)))}{(4 \times (15 - (0 - 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 \times (1 - (5 + (0 - 8))))}{(7 + ((2 \times (6^3)) + 9))} := \frac{(4 \times (1^{508}))}{(7 \times ((2 \times (6 + (3 - 9))))} := \frac{(4 + ((1^5 + 0) \times 8))}{(7 + (2 + (6 - (3 - 9))))} \\ &:= \frac{(4 + ((1 + 50) \times 8))}{(7 \times ((2^6) + 39))} := \frac{(4 + (1 - (5 + (0 - 8))))}{(7 \times (2 - (6 + (3 - 9))))} := \frac{4 + 1508}{7 + 2639} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{71364}{89205} &:= \frac{(((7+1)^3)^6) \times 4}{(((8^9)^2 + 0) \times 5)} &:= \frac{(((7 \times (1+3)) + 6) \times 4)}{((8+9) \times (2 \times (0+5)))} &:= \frac{(((7+1) \times 36) + 4)}{((8-(9^2)) \times (0-5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 - ((1^3) - 6))^4)}{(((8 \times 9)^2 + 0) \times 5)} &:= \frac{((7 - ((1-3) \times 6)) \times 4)}{((8 - (9-20)) \times 5)} &:= \frac{((7 - (1 - (3+6))) \times 4)}{((8 + (9 - (2-0))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 - (1-3)) \times 64)}{((8 \times (9 \times (2 \times (0+5))))))} &:= \frac{((7 \times (1 - (3-6))) + 4)}{((8 \times 9) - (2^{05}))} &:= \frac{((7 + ((1^3) \times 6)) \times 4)}{((8 \times 9) - (2 - (0-5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 + (1 \times (3^6))) \times 4)}{(8 \times (92 \times (0+5)))} &:= \frac{((7 + (1 + (3 \times 6))) \times 4)}{((8 + (9 \times (2-0))) \times 5)} &:= \frac{((7 + (13 \times 6)) \times 4)}{((8+9) \times (20+5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7+13)^{6-4})}{((8 + (92-0)) \times 5)} &:= \frac{((71 - (3-6)) \times 4)}{(((8 \times 9) + (2-0)) \times 5)} &:= \frac{((7-1) \times (36 \times 4))}{(8 \times (9 \times (20-5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((71 + (3 \times 6)) \times 4)}{((8 + (9^2 + 0)) \times 5)} &:= \frac{((71+3) \times (6-4))}{((8 + (9+20)) \times 5)} &:= \frac{(7 - (1 \times (3 - (6 \times 4))))}{(8 - (9 \times (2 + (0-5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 \times (1 - (3 - (6+4))))}{((8 \times 9) - (2 - (0 \times 5)))} &:= \frac{(7 \times (1 \times (36+4)))}{(((8 \times 9) - (2-0)) \times 5)} &:= \frac{(7 \times (1 \times (36-4)))}{(8 \times ((9 - (2-0)) \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + ((1^{36}) - 4))}{((8 - (9 - (2-0))) \times 5)} &:= \frac{(7 + (1 \times (3^{6-4})))}{(8 + (9 - (2 + (0-5))))} &:= \frac{(7 + (1 \times (3 + (6-4))))}{(8 + (9 - (2 - (0 \times 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{7 + 1^{364}}{8+9-2-05} &:= \frac{(7 + (1 + (3 \times (6 \times 4))))}{(8 + (92 - (0 \times 5)))} &:= \frac{(7 + (1 + (36-4)))}{((8 - (9 \times 2)) \times (0-5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (13+64))}{(8 + (92 - (0-5)))} &:= \frac{7136+4}{8920+5} &:= \frac{7136-4}{8920-5}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{74568}{93210} &:= \frac{(((7 \times 4) - (5-6)) \times 8)}{(((9 \times 3) + 2) \times 10)} &:= \frac{(((7 + (4 \times 5))^6) \times 8)}{((9^3)^2 \times 10)} &:= \frac{(((7 + (4-5)) \times 6) + 8)}{((9 \times (3+2)) + 10)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((7-4)^5) \times (6 \times 8))}{((9^3) \times (2 \times 10))} &:= \frac{((7 - (4 - (5 \times 6))) \times 8)}{(9 + (321 - 0))} &:= \frac{((7 - (4 - (5+6))) \times 8)}{((9 + (3+2)) \times 10)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 - (4 - (5-6))) \times 8)}{(9 + (3 - (2-10)))} &:= \frac{((7 - (4 + (5-6))) \times 8)}{(9 + (32 - (1-0)))} &:= \frac{((7 \times (4 \times 5)) - 68)}{(9 \times ((3^2) + (1-0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 \times 4) + ((5+6) \times 8))}{(((9+3)^2) + (1-0))} &:= \frac{((7 + (4 - (5-6))) \times 8)}{((9-3) \times (2 \times 10))} &:= \frac{((7 + (4 \times (5-6))) \times 8)}{((9 - (3 \times 2)) \times 10)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 + (4 + (5 \times 6))) \times 8)}{(9+32) \times 10)} &:= \frac{((7 + (4 + (5-6))) \times 8)}{((9 + (3-2)) \times 10)} &:= \frac{((7 + (4-5)) \times (6 \times 8))}{(((9-3)^2) \times 10)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7+45) \times (6+8))}{((93-2) \times 10)} &:= \frac{((74 - (5-6)) \times 8)}{((9^3) + (21-0))} &:= \frac{((7-4) \times (56+8))}{((9+3) \times (2 \times 10))} \\
 &:= \frac{((74 + (5-6)) \times 8)}{((9^3) + (2 - (1-0)))} &:= \frac{(7 - (4 - (5+68)))}{(93 + (2 \times (1-0)))} &:= \frac{(7 - (4 + (5 - (6+8))))}{(9 + (3 \times (2 \times (1-0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 \times ((4 \times (5-6)) + 8))}{((9 \times (3+2)) - 10)} &:= \frac{(7 + (4 - (5 - (6+8))))}{(9 + ((3 \times 2) + 10))} &:= \frac{(7 + (4 - (5 - (6-8))))}{(9 - (3 + (2 - (1-0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (4 - (5 + (6-8))))}{(9 + (3 - (2 \times (1-0))))} &:= \frac{(7 + (4 + (5 + (6 \times 8))))}{((9 \times (3^2)) - (1-0))} &:= \frac{(7 + (4 + (5+68)))}{(93 + (2+10))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (45+68))}{((9 + (3 \times 2)) \times 10)} &:= \frac{(74 - ((5 \times 6) + 8))}{(9 + (3 \times (2+10)))} &:= \frac{(74 + (5 \times (6+8)))}{((9 + (3^2)) \times 10)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{5342}{186970} &:= \frac{(((5 \times 3) + 4) \times 2)}{(1 + ((8-6) \times 9)) \times 70)} &:= \frac{(((5 \times 3) - 4) \times 2)}{(1 \times ((8 - (6-9)) \times 70))} &:= \frac{(((5^3) - 4) \times 2)}{((1 + (8 \times (6+9))) \times 70)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((5+3) \times 4)^2)}{(1 \times (((8-6)^9) \times 70))} &:= \frac{((5 - (3-4)) \times 2)}{((1 + (8 + (6-9))) \times 70)} &:= \frac{((5 - (3-4))^2)}{(1 \times ((8-6) \times (9 \times 70)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{((5 \times 3) - (4 + 2))}{(((1 + 8) \times 6) - 9) \times (7 - 0)} := \frac{((5 + (3 + 4))^2)}{((18 + (6 \times 9)) \times 70)} := \frac{((5 + 3) \times (4 + 2))}{((1 + (8 + (6 + 9))) \times 70)} \\
 & := \frac{((5 + 34) \times 2)}{(1 \times (((8 \times 6) - 9) \times 70))} := \frac{((5 - 3) \times (4^2))}{(((1^8) + (6 + 9)) \times 70)} := \frac{((53 + 4) \times 2)}{(1 \times (((8 \times 6) + 9) \times 70))} \\
 & := \frac{(5 - (3 - (4^2)))}{((1^{86}) \times (9 \times 70))} := \frac{(5 - (3 - (4 + 2)))}{((1 + ((8 \times 6) - 9)) \times (7 - 0))} := \frac{(5 - (3 - (4 - 2)))}{((1^8) + (69 + 70))} \\
 & := \frac{(5 \times (3 \times (4^2)))}{(1 \times (8 \times ((6 + 9) \times 70)))} := \frac{(5 \times (3 \times (4 + 2)))}{(((1 + 8) \times 6) - 9) \times 70)} := \frac{(5 \times (3 \times (4 - 2)))}{((18 + (6 - 9)) \times 70)} \\
 & := \frac{(5^{3-4+2})}{((1 - (8 \times (6 - 9))) \times (7 - 0))} := \frac{(5 + ((3 + 4) \times 2))}{(1 \times ((86 + 9) \times (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(5 + ((3 + 4)^2))}{((1 + (8 - 6)) \times (9 \times 70))} \\
 & := \frac{(5 + ((3 - 4) \times 2))}{(1 + (8 + (6 \times (9 + (7 - 0))))))} := \frac{(5 + (3 - (4 + 2)))}{(1 \times (8 + (69 - (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(5 + (3 - (4 - 2)))}{((18 - (6 + 9)) \times 70)} \\
 & := \frac{(5 + (3 \times (4 - 2)))}{(((1^8) + (6 \times 9)) \times (7 - 0))} := \frac{(5 + (3^{4-2}))}{(((1^8) + 69) \times (7 - 0))} := \frac{(5 + (3 + (4 \times 2)))}{(1 + ((8 \times 69) + (7 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(5 + (3 + (4^2)))}{((1 + (8 - (6 - 9))) \times 70)} := \frac{(5 + (3 + (4 - 2)))}{(1 \times ((8 + (6 - 9)) \times 70))} := \frac{(5 + (3 + 42))}{((1 - (8 \times (6 - 9))) \times 70)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{6849}{102735}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{((6 \times (8 \times 4)) - 9)}{(10 + 2735)} := \frac{((6 \times (8 - 4)) - 9)}{((1 - (0 - (2 \times 7))) \times (3 \times 5))} := \frac{((6 \times 8) - (4 \times 9))}{(10 \times (2 \times (7 - (3 - 5))))} \\
 & := \frac{((6 \times 8) - (4 + 9))}{((1 - (0 - (2 \times 7))) \times 35)} := \frac{((6 \times 8) + (4 \times 9))}{(10 \times ((2^7) + (3 - 5)))} := \frac{((6 \times 8) + 49)}{((10 \times (2 \times 73)) - 5)} \\
 & := \frac{((6 + (8 + 4)) \times 9)}{((1 - (0 - (2 + 7))) \times (3^5))} := \frac{((6 + (8 - 4)) \times 9)}{(10 \times ((2 + 7) \times (3 \times 5)))} := \frac{((6 + (8 - 4))^9)}{((10^{2+7}) \times (3 \times 5))} \\
 & := \frac{((6 - 8) \times (4 - 9))}{(1 \times (0 + ((27 + 3) \times 5)))} := \frac{(6 - (8 - (4 \times 9)))}{(10 + (2 \times (7 + (3^5))))} := \frac{(6 - (8 - (4 + 9)))}{((10 \times (2^{7-3})) + 5)} \\
 & := \frac{(6 - (8 + (4 - 9)))}{(1 - (0 - (2 + (7 + 35))))} := \frac{(6 - (8 - 49))}{((10 + ((2^7) + 3)) \times 5)} := \frac{(6 \times ((8 \times 4) - 9))}{((10 + (2^7)) \times (3 \times 5))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 \times (8 + (4 - 9)))}{(1 \times (0 + (27 + (3^5))))} := \frac{(6 + ((8 \times 4) - 9))}{(((10 \times (2 + 7)) - 3) \times 5)} := \frac{(6 + ((8 + 4) \times 9))}{((1 + (0 - (2 - (7^3)))) \times 5)} \\
 & := \frac{(6 + ((8 - 4) \times 9))}{((1 - (0 - ((2^7) - 3))) \times 5)} := \frac{(6 + (8 - (4 + 9)))}{((1 + (0 - (2 - (7 - 3)))) \times 5)} := \frac{(6 \times ((8 \times 4) - 9))}{((10 \times 27) + (3 \times 5))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 + (8 + (4 \times 9)))}{((1 - (0 - 2)) \times (7 + (3^5)))} := \frac{(6 + (8 + (4 + 9)))}{(1 \times (0 + (27 \times (3 \times 5))))} := \frac{(6 + (8 + (4 - 9)))}{(1 \times (0 + ((2 + 7) \times (3 \times 5))))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 + (8 + 49))}{(1 \times (0 + (27 \times 35)))} := \frac{(6 + (84 - 9))}{(1 \times (0 - ((2 - 7) \times (3^5))))} := \frac{(68 - (4 \times 9))}{(((10^2) - (7 - 3)) \times 5)} \\
 & := \frac{(68 - (4 - 9))}{((1 - (0 - 2)) \times (73 \times 5))} := \frac{(68 + (4 \times 9))}{(10 \times (2 \times (73 + 5)))} := \frac{(68 + 49)}{((10 - (2 - (7^3))) \times 5)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{9486}{237150}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(((9 + 4) \times 8) + 6)}{(((2^3) \times 7) - 1) \times 50)} := \frac{(((9 - 4) \times 8) - 6)}{((23 - (7 - 1)) \times 50)} := \frac{((9 - (4 - 8)) \times 6)}{((2 + (37 \times 1)) \times 50)} \\
 & := \frac{((9 \times (4 + 8)) + 6)}{(((2^3) \times 7) + 1) \times 50)} := \frac{((9 \times 4) - (8 + 6))}{((2 + (3 + (7 - 1))) \times 50)} := \frac{((9 \times 4) + (8 \times 6))}{(2 \times (3 \times (7 \times (1 \times 50))))} \\
 & := \frac{((9 \times 4) + (8 - 6))}{(((2 \times (3 + 7)) - 1) \times 50)} := \frac{((9 \times 48) + 6)}{((2 + ((3^7) + 1)) \times (5 - 0))} := \frac{((9 + (4 - 8)) \times 6)}{((23 - (7 + 1)) \times 50)} \\
 & := \frac{((9 + (4 - 8))^6)}{((2 + 3)^{7+1^5+0})} := \frac{((9 + 4) \times (8 - 6))}{((2 + (3 + (7 + 1))) \times 50)} := \frac{((9 - 4) \times (8 + 6))}{((2 + 3) \times (7 \times (1 \times 50)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{((9-4) \times (8-6))}{((2-(3-(7-1))) \times 50)} & := \frac{((9-4) \times 86)}{((2+(3 \times 71)) \times 50)} & := \frac{((94 \times 8) - 6)}{((2+371) \times 50)} \\
 & := \frac{(9-(4-(8-6)))}{((2+3) \times (7 \times (1 \times (5-0))))} & := \frac{(9-(4 \times (8-6)))}{((2 \times (3+(7 \times 1))) + (5-0))} & := \frac{(9-(4+(8-6)))}{(2-(3-(71+(5-0))))} \\
 & := \frac{(9 \times ((4 \times 8) - 6))}{((2+37) \times 150)} & := \frac{(9 \times (4-(8-6)))}{((23+7) \times (15-0))} & := \frac{(9 \times (4 \times (8-6)))}{(2 \times (3 \times ((7-1) \times 50)))} \\
 & := \frac{(9 \times (4^{8-6}))}{(2 \times ((37-1) \times 50))} & := \frac{(9+(4-(8-6)))}{(((2^3) \times 7) - 1) \times (5-0)} & := \frac{(9+(4+(8-6)))}{(((2 \times 37) + 1) \times (5-0))} \\
 & := \frac{(94-(8 \times 6))}{((2+(3 \times (7 \times 1))) \times 50)} & := \frac{(94-(8+6))}{((2+(37+1)) \times 50)} & := \frac{(94 \times (8-6))}{((23+71) \times 50)} \\
 & := \frac{(94+(8-6))}{(2 \times (3 \times ((7+1) \times 50)))} & := \frac{(94+86)}{((23+7) \times 150)} & := \frac{(94-86)}{(2+(3 \times (71-(5-0))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.30 31 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{15864}{79320} & := \frac{(((1-(5-8))^6) \times 4)}{(((7+9)^3) \times 20)} & := \frac{(((15-8)^6) \times 4)}{((7^{9-3}) \times 20)} & := \frac{((1-(5-86)) \times 4)}{((79+3) \times 20)} \\
 & := \frac{((1^{586}) + 4)}{(7+(9+(3^2+0)))} & := \frac{((1^5) \times (8 \times (6 \times 4)))}{((7+9) \times (3 \times 20))} & := \frac{((1^5) \times (8+(6-4)))}{(((7+9) \times 3) + (2-0))} \\
 & := \frac{((1^5) + (8+(6+4)))}{((7 \times 9) + (32-0))} & := \frac{((1+(5+(8-6))) \times 4)}{(7-(9 \times (3-20)))} & := \frac{((1+(5+8)) \times (6 \times 4))}{(7 \times ((9+3) \times 20))} \\
 & := \frac{((1+5) \times ((8 \times 6) - 4))}{(((7 \times 9) + 3) \times 20)} & := \frac{(1-(5-(8-(6-4))))}{(7+(9-(3 \times (2-0))))} & := \frac{(1-(5-(8 \times (6+4))))}{((7+(9+3)) \times 20)} \\
 & := \frac{(1-(5-(8+(6+4))))}{(7 \times (9+(3-(2-0))))} & := \frac{(1-(5-(8+(6-4))))}{(7-(9-(32-0)))} & := \frac{(1-(5+(8-64)))}{((7+(9-3)) \times 20)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (((5 \times 8) - 6) \times 4))}{((7+(9 \times 3)) \times 20)} & := \frac{(1 \times (5 \times ((8-6) \times 4))}{((7+93) \times (2-0))} & := \frac{(1 \times (5 \times (8 \times (6+4))))}{((7+93) \times 20)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (5+(8-(6+4))))}{(7-(9+(3-20)))} & := \frac{(1 \times (5+(8 \times (6-4))))}{(7 \times (9+(3 \times (2-0))))} & := \frac{(1+((5 \times 8) - (6 \times 4)))}{(79+(3 \times (2-0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1+(5-(8-(6+4))))}{((7 \times (9-3)) - (2-0))} & := \frac{(1+(5+(8-(6+4))))}{((7-(9-3)) \times 20)} & := \frac{(1+(5+(8+(6+4))))}{(7+(93+20))} \\
 & := \frac{(1+(5+(8+(6-4))))}{(7+(93-20))} & := \frac{(1+(58-(6 \times 4)))}{(7 \times ((9 \times 3) - (2-0)))} & := \frac{(15 \times (8 \times (6-4)))}{(((7 \times 9) - 3) \times 20)} \\
 & := \frac{(15+((8 \times 6) - 4))}{(7+(9 \times (32-0)))} & := \frac{(15+(8^{6-4}))}{(79 \times (3+(2-0)))} & := \frac{(15+(8+(6 \times 4)))}{((79 \times 3) - (2-0))} \\
 & := \frac{(158+(6+4))}{(7 \times ((9-3) \times 20))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16938}{25407} & := \frac{(((1-(6-9))^3) + 8)}{(2 \times (54 - (0 \times 7)))} & := \frac{(((1^6)^9) - (3-8))}{(2 + ((5 - (4-0)) \times 7))} & := \frac{(((1^6) + 9) \times 38)}{(2 \times (5 + (40 \times 7)))} \\
 & := \frac{((1-(6-(9+3))) \times 8)}{((2-5) \times (4 \times (0-7)))} & := \frac{((1-(6-93)) \times 8)}{((2^5) \times (40-7))} & := \frac{((1^6) + (9+38))}{(25+(40+7))} \\
 & := \frac{((1+6) \times ((9-3) \times 8))}{(((2^5) + 40) \times 7)} & := \frac{((1+6) \times (9-(3-8)))}{((25-(4-0)) \times 7)} & := \frac{((16 \times 9) + 38)}{(((2+5) \times 40) - 7)} \\
 & := \frac{((16-9) \times (3 \times 8))}{(((2^5) + (4-0)) \times 7)} & := \frac{(1-(6-((9 \times 3) - 8)))}{((2+(5-(4-0))) \times 7)} & := \frac{(1-(6-(9+(3 \times 8))))}{(((2 \times 5) - (4-0)) \times 7)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(1 - (6 - (9 + 38)))}{(2 + (54 - (0 - 7)))} := \frac{(1 - (6 + (9 \times (3 - 8))))}{((2^5) - (4 \times (0 - 7)))} := \frac{(1 - (6 + (9 - 38)))}{(25 + (4 - (0 - 7)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (69 \times (3 - 8)))}{((2^{5+4+0}) + 7)} := \frac{(1 \times ((6 \times (9 \times 3)) - 8))}{((2 + 5) \times (40 - 7))} := \frac{(1 \times ((6 \times (9 - 3)) + 8))}{(2 \times (5 - (4 \times (0 - 7))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((6 \times 93) - 8))}{(25 \times (40 - 7))} := \frac{(1 \times (6 - (9 + (3 - 8))))}{(2 + (5 - (4 - (0 \times 7))))} := \frac{(1 \times (6 \times ((9 - 3) \times 8)))}{(25 + 407)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (6 \times (9 - (3 - 8))))}{(2 \times ((5 + (4 - 0)) \times 7))} := \frac{(1 \times (6 + (9 - (3 + 8))))}{((2 \times 5) - (4 - (0 \times 7)))} := \frac{(1 \times (6 + (9 - (3 - 8))))}{(2 - (5 - (40 - 7)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (6 + (9 + (3 - 8))))}{(2 + ((5 \times (4 - 0)) - 7))} := \frac{(1 + (((6 + 9) \times 3) - 8))}{(2 + (5 \times (4 - (0 - 7))))} := \frac{(1 + (6 - (9 - (3 \times 8))))}{((2 \times (5 \times (4 - 0))) - 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (6 - (9 - 38)))}{(2 + (5 + (40 + 7)))} := \frac{(16 - (9 + (3 - 8)))}{(2 + (5 + (4 - (0 - 7))))} := \frac{(169 - (3 + 8))}{(2 + (5 \times (40 + 7)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(169 - (3 - 8))}{(254 - (0 - 7))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{17235}{68940}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((1 + 7) \times 2) + 3) \times 5}{((6 + 89) \times (4 - 0))} := \frac{(((1 + 7) \times (2^3)) - 5)}{((68 - 9) \times (4 - 0))} := \frac{((1 - (7 - 23)) \times 5)}{(68 \times (9 - (4 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (7 \times 2)) \times (3 \times 5))}{(6 + (894 - 0))} := \frac{(1 - (7 - (23 \times 5)))}{((6 \times (8 \times 9)) + (4 - 0))} := \frac{(1 - (7 + (2 - 35)))}{(6 + (8 + (94 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (((7^2) \times 3) + 5))}{((68 \times 9) - (4 - 0))} := \frac{(1 \times (((7^2) - 3) \times 5))}{((6 + (8 + 9)) \times 40)} := \frac{(1 \times ((7 \times 23) - 5))}{(6 \times (8 \times (9 + (4 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((7 + (2 + 3)) \times 5))}{(6 \times (8 \times (9 - (4 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 \times ((72 \times 3) + 5))}{(68 \times (9 + (4 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 \times (7 - (2 - (3 - 5))))}{((6 \times 8) - (9 \times (4 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (7 - (2 + (3 - 5))))}{((6 - (8 - 9)) \times (4 - 0))} := \frac{(1 \times (7 \times (2 + (3 + 5))))}{((6 - (8 - 9)) \times 40)} := \frac{(1 \times (7 \times (23 - 5)))}{((6 + 8) \times (9 \times (4 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (7 + (2 \times (3 + 5))))}{(6 - (8 - (94 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 \times (7 + (2 \times 35)))}{((68 + 9) \times (4 - 0))} := \frac{(1 \times (7 + (2 + (3^5))))}{(68 + 940)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (72 - (3 \times 5)))}{(((6 \times 8) + 9) \times (4 - 0))} := \frac{(1 \times (72 + 35))}{((6 \times (8 \times 9)) - (4 - 0))} := \frac{(1 + (((7^2) \times 3) + 5))}{(6 \times (8 + (94 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (((7^2) \times 3) - 5))}{((68 \times 9) - 40)} := \frac{(1 + ((7 \times 2) + 35))}{((6 + (8 - 9)) \times 40)} := \frac{(1 + ((7 + (2 \times 3)) \times 5))}{(6 \times (8 + (9 \times (4 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (7 - ((2^3) - 5)))}{((6 + (8 - 9)) \times (4 - 0))} := \frac{(1 + (7 - (2 - (3 \times 5))))}{((6 \times 8) + (9 \times (4 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + (7 - (2 + (3 - 5))))}{(68 - (9 \times (4 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (7 + ((2^3) \times 5)))}{(6 \times ((8 \times 9) - 40))} := \frac{(1 + (7 + (2 \times 35)))}{((6 + (8 \times 9)) \times (4 - 0))} := \frac{(1 + (7 + (23 - 5)))}{(68 + (9 \times (4 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(17 + (2 + 35))}{(6^{8-9+4+0})}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{21390}{74865}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((2 - (1 - 3)) \times (9 - 0))}{(7 \times (48 - (6 \times 5)))} := \frac{((2 \times (1 + 3)) + 90)}{(7^{4 \times (8-6)-5})} := \frac{((2 \times (1 - 3)) + 90)}{(7 \times ((4 \times 8) + (6 + 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (1 + 3)) \times (9 - 0))}{(74 + (86 \times 5))} := \frac{((2 \times (1 + 3)) + 90)}{(7 + (4 \times (86 + 5)))} := \frac{(2 - ((1^3) - (9 - 0)))}{(7 + (4 \times (8 - (6 - 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (1 - (3 \times (9 - 0))))}{(7 \times (4 + ((8 - 6) \times 5)))} := \frac{(2 - (1 - (3 + 90)))}{(7 \times (4 + ((8 \times 6) - 5)))} := \frac{(2 - (1 \times (3 - (9 - 0))))}{(7 + ((4^{8-6}) + 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((1^3) \times 90))}{(7 \times ((4 + (8 + 6)) \times 5))} := \frac{(2 \times ((1^3) + (9 - 0)))}{(7 \times ((4 - (8 - 6)) \times 5))} := \frac{(2 \times ((1 + 3) \times (9 - 0)))}{(7 \times (4 \times (8 + (6 - 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((1 + 3) \times 90))}{(7 \times ((4 + 8) \times (6 \times 5)))} := \frac{(2 \times ((1 + 3)^9 + 0))}{(7 \times (4^{8+6-5}))} := \frac{(2 \times (1 - (3 - (9 - 0))))}{(7 \times (4 - (8 - (6 + 5))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (1 \times (3 \times 90)))}{(7 \times ((48 + 6) \times 5))} := \frac{(2 \times (1 \times (3 + (9 - 0))))}{(7 + (4 + (8 + 65)))} := \frac{(2 \times (1 \times (39 - 0)))}{((7 - 4) \times (86 + 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (1 + (3 \times (9 - 0))))}{(7 \times (4 \times (8 - (6 - 5))))} := \frac{(2 \times (1 + (3 + (9 - 0))))}{(7 \times (4 + (8 + (6 - 5))))} := \frac{(2 \times (1 + (39 - 0)))}{(7 \times (4 \times ((8 - 6) \times 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2^{1^{39+0}})}{(7^{4+8-6-5})} := \frac{(2 \times (13 - (9 - 0)))}{(7 - (4 - ((8 \times 6) + 5)))} := \frac{(2 + ((1^3) + (9 - 0)))}{(74 - ((8 - 6)^5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (1 - (3 - 90)))}{((7 + (4 \times (8 + 6))) \times 5)} := \frac{(2 + (1 + (3 + 90)))}{(7 \times (48 \times (6 - 5)))} := \frac{(2 + (1 + (39 - 0)))}{(7 \times ((4^8-6) + 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (13 - (9 - 0)))}{(7 + (4 + ((8 - 6) \times 5)))} := \frac{(2 + 1390)}{(7 + 4865)} := \frac{(21 + (3 + 90))}{(7 \times (4 + ((8 \times 6) + 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(21 + (39 - 0))}{(7 \times ((4 + (8 - 6)) \times 5))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{67124}{83905}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((6 \times (7 \times 1))^2) - 4)}{(8 \times ((3 \times 90) + 5))} := \frac{(((6 \times (7 \times 1)) - 2)^4)}{((8 + (3 + (9 - 0)))^5)} := \frac{(((6 \times 71) - 2) \times 4)}{(8 \times ((3 \times 90) - 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((6 + (7 - 1))^2) - 4)}{((8 + (3 \times (9 - 0))) \times 5)} := \frac{((6 \times ((7 + 1)^2)) - 4)}{((8 - (3 - 90)) \times 5)} := \frac{((6 \times ((7 - 1) \times 2)) + 4)}{((8 - (3 \times 9)) \times (0 - 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 \times (7 - (1^2))) + 4)}{(8 + (3 \times (9 + 05)))} := \frac{((6 \times (7 - (1^2))) - 4)}{(8 + ((3 \times (9 - 0)) + 5))} := \frac{((6 \times (7 \times 12)) - 4)}{((8 - 3)^{9-05})} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 + (7 + (1^2))) \times 4)}{((8 - (3 - (9 - 0))) \times 5)} := \frac{((67 + 1) \times 24)}{(8 \times (3 \times (90 - 5)))} := \frac{((67 - 1) \times (2 + 4))}{((8 + 3) \times (9 \times (0 + 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 - (7 - ((1 + 2)^4)))}{(8 - (3 - (90 + 5)))} := \frac{(6 - (7 - (1 + (2^4))))}{(8 + (3 \times (9 + (0 - 5))))} := \frac{(6 - (7 - (1 + 24)))}{(8 + ((3 \times (9 - 0)) - 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 - (7 \times (1 \times (2 - 4))))}{(8 + (3 + (9 + 05)))} := \frac{(6 - (7 + (1 - (2 + 4))))}{(8 - (3 - (9 \times (0 \times 5))))} := \frac{(6 \times ((7 + 1) \times (2 \times 4)))}{(8 \times ((3 + (9 - 0)) \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times ((7 + 12) \times 4))}{(((8 \times 3) + 90) \times 5)} := \frac{(6 \times ((7 - 1) \times 24))}{(8 \times (3 \times (9 \times (0 + 5))))} := \frac{(6 \times (7 - (1 - (2^4))))}{(((8 \times 3) + (9 - 0)) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (7 - (1 - (2 + 4))))}{(8 - (3 - (90 - 5)))} := \frac{(6 \times (7 - (1 - 24)))}{((8 - 3) \times (9 \times (0 + 5)))} := \frac{(6 \times (7 + (1 - (2 - 4))))}{(((8 \times 3) - (9 - 0)) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (7 + (1 + 24)))}{(8 \times ((3 - 9) \times (0 - 5)))} := \frac{(6 + (7 - (1 - (2^4))))}{(8 + (3 \times (9 - (0 \times 5))))} := \frac{(6 + (7 - (1 - 24)))}{((8 - 3) \times (9 - (0 \times 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 + (7 + (1 - (2 + 4))))}{((8 + (3 - (9 - 0))) \times 5)} := \frac{(6 + (7 + (1 + (2 - 4))))}{(8 + (3 + (9 + (0 - 5))))} := \frac{6712 + 4}{8390 + 5} \\
 &:= \frac{6712 - 4}{8390 - 5}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{67140}{83925}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((6 \times 7) + 1) \times (4 - 0))}{(((8 - 3) \times 9) - 2) \times 5)} := \frac{(((6 \times 7) - 1) \times (4 - 0))}{((8 + (3 \times (9 + 2))) \times 5)} := \frac{((6 \times (7 + 1)) - (4 - 0))}{(((8 - 3) \times 9) + (2 \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 \times (7 + 1)) + 40)}{(8 + (3 \times (9 + 25)))} := \frac{((6 \times (7 - 1)) - (4 - 0))}{(8 \times (3 + (9 - (2 + 5))))} := \frac{((6 \times (7 - 1)) + 40)}{(8 - (3 - (9 \times (2 \times 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6^7-1) \times (4 - 0))}{(((8 \times (3 \times 9))^2) \times 5)} := \frac{((6 + (7 + 1)) \times (4 - 0))}{(83 - ((9 \times 2) - 5))} := \frac{((6 + 71) \times (4 - 0))}{((8 + 3) \times ((9 - 2) \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((67 - 1) \times (4 - 0))}{(((8 \times 3) + 9) \times (2 \times 5))} := \frac{(6 - (7 - (1 + (4 - 0))))}{(8 + (3 - (9 + (2 - 5))))} := \frac{(6 - (7 - (1 + 40)))}{(8 + (39 - (2 - 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times ((7 + 1) \times (4 - 0)))}{(8 \times (3 - (9 \times (2 - 5))))} := \frac{(6 \times ((7 + 1) \times 40))}{(8 \times ((3 + 9) \times 25))} := \frac{(6 \times ((7 - 1) \times (4 - 0)))}{(83 + (92 + 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times ((7 - 1)^4 + 0))}{(8 \times (3 \times ((9^2) \times 5)))} := \frac{(6 \times (7 - (1 - (4 - 0))))}{((8 \times (3 + (9 - 2))) - 5)} := \frac{(6 \times (7 - (1^4 + 0)))}{(8 + (3 + (9 + 25)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (7 \times (1 \times (4 - 0))))}{(((8 \times 3) + (9 \times 2)) \times 5)} := \frac{(6 \times (7 \times (1 \times 40)))}{(((8^3) - 92) \times 5)} := \frac{(6 \times (7 + (1 - (4 - 0))))}{(8 + (3 + (9 + (2 \times 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (7 + (1^4 + 0)))}{((8 - (3 - (9 - 2))) \times 5)} := \frac{(6 \times (7 + (1 + (4 - 0))))}{((8 + (3 + (9 - 2))) \times 5)} := \frac{(6 \times (7 + (1 + 40)))}{((83 - (9 + 2)) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 + (7 - (1 - (4 - 0))))}{((8 + (3 - (9 - 2))) \times 5)} := \frac{(6 + (7 - (1^4 + 0)))}{(8 + (39 - (2^5)))} := \frac{(6 + (7 - (1 + (4 - 0))))}{(8 + (3 + (9 - (2 \times 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 + (7 - (1 - 40)))}{(8 + (3 \times (9 + (2 \times 5))))} := \frac{(67 + (1 - (4 - 0)))}{((8 - (3 - (9 + 2))) \times 5)} := \frac{(67 + (1^4 + 0))}{((8 \times (3 + (9 - 2))) + 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(67 + (1 - 40))}{(((8 + (3 + 9)) \times 2) - 5)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{76184}{95230}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((7 - (6 - 1))^8) + 4)}{(95 + 230)} := \frac{(((7 \times 6) - (1 + 8)) \times 4)}{(9 + (52 \times (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(((7 \times 6) + (1 + 8)) \times 4)}{((9 \times (5^2)) + 30)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((7 + 61) \times 8) - 4)}{(9 \times ((5^2) \times (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(((7 - (6 - (1 + 8))) \times 4)}{((9 \times 5) + (2 + (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(((7 \times ((6 + 1) \times 8)) + 4)}{(9 \times (52 + (3 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 \times 6) - (18 - 4))}{(95 - (2 \times 30))} := \frac{((7 + (6 - (1 \times 8))) \times 4)}{(((9 + 5) \times 2) - (3 - 0))} := \frac{((7 + (6 - (1^8))) \times 4)}{((9 - (5 + 2)) \times 30)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 + (6 - (1 - 8))) \times 4)}{(95 + (2 + (3 - 0)))} := \frac{((7 + (6 \times (1 \times 8))) \times 4)}{((9 \times 5) + 230)} := \frac{((7 + (6 \times 1)) \times (8 + 4))}{((9 \times (5^2)) - 30)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 + (6 + (1^8))) \times 4)}{((9 + 5) \times (2 + (3 - 0)))} := \frac{((7 + (6 + 18)) \times 4)}{(95 + (2 \times 30))} := \frac{((7 + (6 - 1)) \times (8 \times 4))}{((9 + (5 + 2)) \times 30)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 + (6 - 1)) \times (8 + 4))}{((9 - (5 - 2)) \times 30)} := \frac{((7 + 6) \times ((1 + 8) \times 4))}{(9 \times (5 + (2 \times 30)))} := \frac{((7 + 61) \times (8 + 4))}{((9 + (5^2)) \times 30)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 - (6 + (1 - (8 \times 4))))}{((9 \times 5) - (2 + (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(7 - (6 + (1 - (8 - 4))))}{(9 - (5 + (2 - (3 - 0))))} := \frac{(7 - (6 + (1 - 84)))}{((9 \times 5) + (2 \times 30))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 \times ((6 + 18) \times 4))}{((9 + 5) \times (2 \times 30))} := \frac{(7 \times (6 \times ((1 + 8) \times 4)))}{(9 \times ((5 + 2) \times 30))} := \frac{(7 + (6 - (1 - (8 + 4))))}{((9 \times (5 - 2)) + (3 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (6 - (1 - (8 - 4))))}{(9 + (5 + (2 \times (3 - 0))))} := \frac{(7 + (6 - (1^{84})))}{(9 + (5 - (2 - (3 - 0))))} := \frac{(7 + (6 - (1 + (8 - 4))))}{(9 - (5 - (2 \times (3 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(76 \times (1 + (8 - 4)))}{((9 \times (5 \times 2)) + 30)} := \frac{(76 \times (1 + (8 - 4)))}{(9 \times (5 + (2 + (3 - 0))))} := \frac{(76 \times (1 \times (8 \times 4)))}{(95 \times (2 + 30))} \\
 &:= \frac{(76 \times (1 + (8 - 4)))}{(95 \times (2 + (3 - 0)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{5823}{174690}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((5 \times 8) - 2) \times 3)}{(((1 + 7) \times 4) + 6) \times 90)} := \frac{(((5 + 8)^2) \times 3)}{((1 + (7 \times (4 \times 6))) \times 90)} := \frac{((5 \times (8 - 2)) - 3)}{(1 \times ((7 - (4 - 6)) \times 90))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 \times 8) - (2 \times 3))}{(17 \times (4 \times (6 + (9 - 0))))} := \frac{((5^{8-2}) \times 3)}{(((1^7) + 4)^6) \times 90)} := \frac{((5 + (8^2)) \times 3)}{((1 + (74 - 6)) \times 90)} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 + (8 - 2)) \times 3)}{(((1^7) + (4 + 6)) \times 90)} := \frac{((5 + 8) \times (2 \times 3))}{(((1 + 7) \times 4) - 6) \times 90)} := \frac{((5 + 8) \times 23)}{((17 - 4) \times 690)} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 - (8 - (2 \times 3)))}{((1^{746}) \times 90)} := \frac{(5 - (8 - (2 + 3)))}{(1 - (7 + ((4 \times 6) - 90)))} := \frac{(5 - (8 \times (2 - 3)))}{((1 - 7) \times (4 - (69 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times (8 - (2 \times 3)))}{((1 - 7) \times (4 - (6 \times (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(5 \times (8 - (2 + 3)))}{(1 \times ((7 + (4 - 6)) \times 90))} := \frac{(5 \times (8 - (2 - 3)))}{((1 - (7 \times (4 - 6))) \times 90)} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times (8 \times (2 \times 3)))}{(1 \times ((74 + 6) \times 90))} := \frac{(5 + ((8 \times 2) + 3))}{(1 \times ((74 + 6) \times (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(5 + ((8^2) + 3))}{((1 + (7 - 4)) \times (6 \times 90))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(5 + ((8^2) - 3))}{(1 \times (((7 \times 4) - 6) \times 90))} &:= \frac{(5 + ((8 - 2) \times 3))}{((1^{74}) \times 690)} &:= \frac{(5 + (8 - (2 \times 3)))}{(1 - (7 - (4 \times (6 \times (9 - 0))))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (8 - (2 - 3)))}{(1 \times (7 \times (4 \times (6 + (9 - 0))))))} &:= \frac{(5 + (8 \times (2^3)))}{(1 \times ((7 - 4) \times 690))} &:= \frac{(5 + (8 \times 23))}{((17 + 46) \times 90)} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (8 + (2^3)))}{(1 \times (7 \times ((4 + 6) \times (9 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(5 + (8 + (2 + 3)))}{((1 + (7 + (4 - 6))) \times 90)} &:= \frac{(5 + (8 + (2 - 3)))}{((1 - (7 - 46)) \times (9 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (8 + 23))}{((1 - 7) \times ((4 - 6) \times 90))} &:= \frac{(5 + (82 + 3))}{(((1^7) + 4) \times (6 \times 90))} &:= \frac{(58 + (2 - 3))}{((1 + ((7 - 4) \times 6)) \times 90)} \\
 &:= \frac{(58 + 23)}{((17 + (4 + 6)) \times 90)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{7293}{145860}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((7^2) + 9) \times 3)}{((1^4) \times (58 \times 60))} &:= \frac{(((7^2) - 9) \times 3)}{((1^4) \times (5 \times (8 \times 60)))} &:= \frac{(((7 - 2) \times 9) + 3)}{(1 \times (4 \times (5 \times (8 \times (6 - 0))))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((7 - 2)^9) \times 3)}{((1 + 4) \times ((5^8) \times 60))} &:= \frac{(((7 - (2 - 9)) \times 3)}{(((1^4) + (5 + 8)) \times 60)} &:= \frac{(((7 \times (2 \times 9)) - 3)}{(((1^4) + (5 \times 8)) \times 60)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 \times 2) - (9 + 3))}{(1 \times (4 \times (5 \times (8 - (6 - 0))))))} &:= \frac{((7 \times 2) + (9 - 3))}{(1 \times (4 \times ((5 \times 8) + 60)))} &:= \frac{((7^2) - (9 - 3))}{(1 + (4 - (5 - 860)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7^2) + (9 - 3))}{((145 \times 8) - 60)} &:= \frac{((7 + (2 + 9)) \times 3)}{((1 + (4 + (5 + 8))) \times 60)} &:= \frac{((7 + 29) \times 3)}{(1 \times (45 \times (8 \times (6 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 - 2) \times (9 \times 3))}{((1 + (4 + (5 \times 8))) \times 60)} &:= \frac{((7 - 2) \times (9 - 3))}{((1 - (4 - (5 + 8))) \times 60)} &:= \frac{((72 - 9) \times 3)}{((1 + (4 + 58)) \times 60)} \\
 &:= \frac{((1^4) \times (5 \times (8 + 60)))}{(7 \times (2 \times (9 - 3)))} &:= \frac{((1 \times ((4 \times (5 \times 8)) + 60))}{(7 + (2 - (9 - 3)))} &:= \frac{((14 \times (5 \times (8 \times (6 - 0))))}{(7 + (2 \times (9 \times 3)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 \times (((4 \times 5) + 8) \times 60))}{(7 + (2 \times (9^3)))} &:= \frac{((1 - (4 + (5 - (8 + 60))))}{(7 + (2 \times (9 + 3)))} &:= \frac{((145 \times 8) + 60)}{((145 \times 8) + 60)} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + 4) \times 5860)}{((1 + 4) \times 5860)} &:= \frac{((7 + (2 \times (9 + 3)))}{((14 \times (5 \times 8)) + 60)} &:= \frac{((7 + (2 + (9 \times 3)))}{(1 \times (((4 \times 5) - 8) \times 60))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (2 + (9 + 3)))}{(1 \times ((4 - (5 - 8)) \times 60))} &:= \frac{(7 + (2 + (9 - 3)))}{(1 \times ((45 \times 8) - 60))} &:= \frac{(7 + (29 + 3))}{((1 - (4 \times (5 - 8))) \times 60)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (29 - 3))}{((14 + (5 - 8)) \times 60)} &:= \frac{(72 - (9 + 3))}{((1 + 4) \times (5 \times (8 \times (6 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(72 + (9 \times 3))}{(((1 + 4) \times 5) + 8) \times 60)} \\
 &:= \frac{(72 + 93)}{((1 - (4 - 58)) \times 60)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{7329}{146580}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((7 + 3) \times 2) + 9)}{(1 \times (4 \times (65 + 80)))} &:= \frac{((7 - (3 \times 2)) \times 9)}{(1 \times ((4 \times 65) - 80))} &:= \frac{((7 - (3 \times 2))^9)}{(1 + (4 - (65 - 80)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 - (3 + 2)) \times 9)}{((1 + (4 \times (6 + 5))) \times (8 - 0))} &:= \frac{((7 \times (3 + 2)) + 9)}{((7 \times (3 + 2)) + 9)} &:= \frac{((7 \times (3 + 2)) - 9)}{((7 \times (3 + 2)) - 9)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 \times 3) + (2 + 9))}{((1 + (4 \times (6 + 5))) \times (8 - 0))} &:= \frac{((7 \times 3) + (2 - 9))}{((1 - ((4 - 6) \times 5)) \times 80)} &:= \frac{((1^4) \times (65 \times (8 - 0)))}{((7 \times 3) + 29)} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 - (4 - (6 + 5))) \times 80)}{((7 + (3 + 2)) \times 9)} &:= \frac{((7 \times 3) + (2 - 9))}{((1 + (4 + (6 \times 5))) \times (8 - 0))} &:= \frac{((1 + (4 \times 6)) \times (5 \times (8 - 0)))}{((7 + 3) \times 29)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 + (3 + 2)) \times 9)}{((1 - (4 - (6 \times 5))) \times 80)} &:= \frac{((7 + 3) \times (2 \times 9))}{((1 + (4 \times (6 + 5))) \times 80)} &:= \frac{((7 + 3) \times 29)}{(1 \times ((4 + 6) \times 580))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 - 3) \times 29)}{(1 \times (((4 \times 6) + 5) \times 80))} &:= \frac{(7 - ((3 \times 2) - 9))}{(1 \times ((4 \times (6 \times 5)) + 80))} &:= \frac{(7 - ((3 - 2)^9))}{(1 \times ((4 + (6 + 5)) \times (8 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 - (3 - (2 \times 9)))}{(1 \times (4 \times ((6 \times 5) + 80)))} &:= \frac{(7 - (3 \times (2 - 9)))}{((1 + (4 + 65)) \times (8 - 0))} &:= \frac{(7 + ((3 \times 2) - 9))}{((1^4 \times (6 - 5)) \times 80)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(7 + ((3^2) + 9))}{((14 \times (6 \times 5)) + 80)} &:= \frac{(7 + ((3 + 2) \times 9))}{((14 - (6 - 5)) \times 80)} &:= \frac{(7 + ((3 - 2) \times 9))}{(1 \times (4 \times ((6 - 5) \times 80)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + ((3 - 2)^9))}{((1 + ((4 \times 6) - 5)) \times (8 - 0))} &:= \frac{(7 + (3 - (2 - 9)))}{(1 \times ((4 \times 65) + 80))} &:= \frac{(7 + (3 \times (2 + 9)))}{((14 + 6) \times (5 \times (8 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (3 \times 29))}{((1 + 46) \times (5 \times (8 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(7 + (3 + (2 + 9)))}{(14 + (6 + (5 \times 80)))} &:= \frac{(7 + (3 + (2 - 9)))}{(1 + (46 + (5 + (8 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (32 + 9))}{(1 \times (4 \times (6 \times (5 \times (8 - 0)))))} &:= \frac{(7 + (32 - 9))}{(14 + (6 + 580))} &:= \frac{(73 - (2 - 9))}{((1 + ((4 \times 6) - 5)) \times 80)} \\
 &:= \frac{(73 + 29)}{(1 \times (4 \times (6 \times (5 + 80))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.31 32 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13458}{67290} &:= \frac{(((1 - (3 - 4)) \times 5) + 8)}{((6 - (7 - 2)) \times 90)} &:= \frac{(((1 + 3)^4) - 58)}{((6 + (7 - 2)) \times 90)} &:= \frac{1^{345} + 8}{6 \times (7 + 2) - 9 + 0} \\
 &:= \frac{((1^3) \times ((4 + 5) \times 8))}{(((6 \times 7) - 2) \times (9 - 0))} &:= \frac{((1^3) + (45 + 8))}{(6 \times ((7 - 2) \times (9 - 0)))} &:= \frac{((1 + (3 \times 4)) \times 58)}{((6 + 7) \times 290)} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (3 + (4 - 5))) \times 8)}{((6 \times (7 - 2)) + 90)} &:= \frac{((1 + 3) \times ((4 \times 5)^8))}{((6 + (7 \times 2))^9 + 0)} &:= \frac{((13 - 4) \times (5 \times 8))}{((6 + (7 \times 2)) \times 90)} \\
 &:= \frac{((13 - 4) \times (5 + 8))}{((67 - 2) \times (9 - 0))} &:= \frac{((1 - 34) \times (5 - 8))}{((6 + (7^2)) \times (9 - 0))} &:= \frac{(1 - ((3 \times 4) - (5 \times 8)))}{(6 + ((7^2) + 90))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (3 - ((4 \times 5) + 8)))}{((6 \times 7) - (2 - 90))} &:= \frac{(1 - (3 \times ((4 - 5) \times 8)))}{((67 \times 2) - (9 - 0))} &:= \frac{(1 - (3 + ((4 - 5) \times 8)))}{(6 \times ((7 \times 2) - (9 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (3 + (4 - (5 + 8))))}{(((6 + 7) \times 2) + (9 - 0))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (((3 + 4) \times 5) - 8))}{((6 + (7 + 2)) \times (9 - 0))} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((3 - (4 - 5)) \times 8))}{(((6 + 7)^2) - (9 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (3 - (4 - (5 + 8))))}{(67 + (2 - (9 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (3 - (4 \times (5 - 8))))}{((6 \times (7 \times 2)) - (9 - 0))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (3 - (4 + (5 - 8))))}{(6 - (7 - (2 + (9 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(67 + (2 - (9 - 0)))}{(1 \times (3 - (4 - 58)))} &:= \frac{(6 + (7 + (2 + 90)))}{(1 \times (3 \times (4 - (5 - 8))))} &:= \frac{(67 - (2 - 90))}{(1 \times (3 + ((4 \times 5) + 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 \times (7^2)) - (9 - 0))}{(1 + ((3 \times (4 + 5)) + 8))} &:= \frac{(6 + (7 + (2 + 90)))}{(1 + ((3 + (4 - 5)) \times 8))} &:= \frac{(67 - (2 - 90))}{(1 + (3 \times (4 - (5 - 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + ((3 \times (4 + 5)) + 8))}{((6 + (7 \times 2)) \times (9 - 0))} &:= \frac{(67 + (2 \times (9 - 0)))}{(6 + ((7 \times 2) + 90))} &:= \frac{(6 + ((7 \times 2) + 90))}{(6 + ((7^2) - (9 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (3^{4+5-8}))}{(6 + (7 - (2 - (9 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(1 + (3 + (4 - (5 - 8))))}{(6 - (7 \times (2 - (9 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(1 + (3 + (4 + (5 \times 8))))}{(6 \times ((7^2) - (9 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(13 + (4 + (5 + 8)))}{(6 \times (7 + (2 \times (9 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(134 + (5 + 8))}{(6 + (729 - 0))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20817}{34695} &:= \frac{(((2 \times (0 + 8)) - 1) \times 7)}{((3 \times (4 \times (6 + 9))) - 5)} &:= \frac{((2 - (0 - (8 - 1))) \times 7)}{(3 \times ((4 - (6 - 9)) \times 5))} &:= \frac{((2 \times (0 \times 8)) - (1 - 7))}{((3 - (4 + (6 - 9))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (0 + (8 - 1))) + 7)}{(3 - (4 \times (6 - (9 + 5))))} &:= \frac{((2 \times (0 + 8)) + (1 + 7))}{(((3 - (4 - 6)) \times 9) - 5)} &:= \frac{((2^{08-1}) + 7)}{((3 - (4 - 6)) \times (9 \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^{08}) + (1 + 7))}{((34 + (6 \times 9)) \times 5)} &:= \frac{((2 + (0 - 8)) \times (1 - 7))}{(3 \times ((4 \times 6) - (9 - 5)))} &:= \frac{((20 \times (8 \times 1)) - 7)}{(3 \times ((4 + 6) \times 9) - 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((20 \times (8 - 1)) + 7)}{((34 + (6 + 9)) \times 5)} &:= \frac{((20 \times 8) - (1^7))}{((3 - (4 - (6 \times 9))) \times 5)} &:= \frac{((20 + (8 - 1)) \times 7)}{(3 \times (4 + (6 + 95)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((20 - 8) \times 17)}{(3 - (4 - 69)) \times 5} &:= \frac{((208 - 1) \times 7)}{(3 + 4) \times (69 \times 5)} &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - ((8 - 1) \times 7)))}{(34 + (6 + (9 \times 5)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (8 - (1 \times 7))))}{(3 + (4 - (6 - (9 - 5))))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (8 - (1^7))))}{(3 + (4 - (6 - (9 + 5))))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (8 \times (1 + 7))))}{((3 + (4 + (6 + 9))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (8 + 17)))}{(3 + (46 - (9 - 5)))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (81 + 7)))}{(3 \times (46 + (9 - 5)))} := \frac{(2 \times ((0 \times 8) - (1 - 7)))}{((3 + (4 + (6 - 9))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 - (8 \times (1 - 7))))}{((3 \times (46 + 9)) - 5)} := \frac{(2 \times (0 - (8 - 17)))}{(3 \times ((4 \times 6) - (9 + 5)))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (8 + (1 \times 7))))}{(3 - (4 - (6 + (9 \times 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (81 \times 7)))}{((3 + 4) \times (6 \times (9 \times 5)))} := \frac{(20 \times (8 + (1 \times 7)))}{(((3^4) \times 6) + (9 + 5))} := \frac{(20 \times (8 + (1^7)))}{(((3^4) - 6) \times (9 - 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(20 + (8 \times (1 + 7)))}{((3^4) + ((6 \times 9) + 5))} := \frac{(20 + (8 + 17))}{((3 - (4 \times (6 - 9))) \times 5)} := \frac{(20 + (81 + 7))}{(3 \times (46 + (9 + 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(20 + 817)}{(3 + (4 \times 69)) \times 5} := \frac{(208 + (1 + 7))}{(346 + (9 + 5))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{24318}{60795}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((2 \times 4)^3) - 18)}{((6 - (0 - 7)) \times 95)} := \frac{(((2^4) + (3 \times 1)) \times 8)}{((60 + (7 + 9)) \times 5)} := \frac{((2 \times ((4^3) + 1)) + 8)}{((6 - (0 - (7 \times 9))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + (4 + (3 \times 1))) \times 8)}{((6^{-07+9}) \times 5)} := \frac{((2 + 4) \times 318)}{(6 \times (0 + 795))} := \frac{(2 - (4 - (31 \times 8)))}{((60 + (7 \times 9)) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((4 \times 31) + 8))}{(60 \times (7 + (9 - 5)))} := \frac{(2 \times ((43 - 1) \times 8))}{(60 \times (7 \times (9 - 5)))} := \frac{(2 \times (4 - (3 - (1 + 8))))}{(60 + ((7 - 9) \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (4 - (3 - 18)))}{((6 \times (0 \times 7)) + 95)} := \frac{(2 \times (4 \times (3 - (1^8))))}{((6 + (0 - (7 - 9))) \times 5)} := \frac{(2 \times (4 \times (3 \times (1 \times 8))))}{(6 \times (0 + ((7 + 9) \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (4 \times (3 \times (1^8))))}{(6 \times (0 - ((7 - 9) \times 5)))} := \frac{(2 \times (4 \times (3 + (1 \times 8))))}{((60 - (7 + 9)) \times 5)} := \frac{(2 \times (4^{3-1^8}))}{(6 - (0 - (79 - 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (4 + (3 - (1^8))))}{(6 \times ((0 \times 79) + 5))} := \frac{(2 \times (4 + (3 - (1 - 8))))}{(60 - ((7 - 9) \times 5))} := \frac{(2 \times (4 + (3 \times (1 \times 8))))}{(60 + ((7 + 9) \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (4 + (3 \times 18)))}{((60 + (7 - 9)) \times 5)} := \frac{(2 \times (4 + (3 + (1 \times 8))))}{((6 - ((0 \times 7) - 9)) \times 5)} := \frac{(2 \times (4 + (31 \times 8)))}{(60 \times (7 + (9 + 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (43 + (1 \times 8)))}{(((6 \times (0 + 7)) + 9) \times 5)} := \frac{(2^{4-3+1^8})}{(6 - ((0 \times 7) - (9 - 5)))} := \frac{(2^{4-3 \times 1^8})}{((6 \times (0 \times 79)) + 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + ((4^3-1) \times 8))}{((60 \times 7) - 95)} := \frac{(2 + (4^{3-1^8}))}{((6 \times (0 \times 7)) + (9 \times 5))} := \frac{(2 + (4^{3 \times 1^8}))}{(((6 \times (0 + 7)) - 9) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (4 + (3 - (1^8))))}{((6 - (0 - (7 - 9))) \times 5)} := \frac{(2 + (43 - (1^8)))}{((6 - (0 - (7 + 9))) \times 5)} := \frac{(2 + (43 - (1 + 8)))}{(6 - (0 - (79 + 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(24 + 318)}{(60 + 795)} := \frac{(243 - (1 + 8))}{((6 - (0 - 7)) \times (9 \times 5))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{24876}{31095}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((2^4) \times 8) + 76)}{(3 \times ((10 \times 9) - 5))} := \frac{(((2^4) \times 8) - 76)}{((3 + (1 + 09)) \times 5)} := \frac{(((2 + 4) \times 8) + 76)}{(31 \times ((0 \times 9) + 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 - (4 - (8 \times 7))) \times 6)}{(310 + 95)} := \frac{((2 - (4 - 8)) \times (7 \times 6))}{(3 \times (10 + 95))} := \frac{((2 \times ((4 \times 8) + 7)) + 6)}{(((3 \times 10) - 9) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (4 + (8 + 7))) + 6)}{((3 - (1 + (0 - 9))) \times 5)} := \frac{((2 \times (4 + 8)) + 76)}{((3 \times 10) + 95)} := \frac{((2 \times 48) + 76)}{(310 - 95)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^{4 \times (8-7)}) \times 6)}{(3 \times (10 \times (9 - 5)))} := \frac{((2^4) \times ((8 \times 7) + 6))}{(310 \times (9 - 5))} := \frac{((2^4) \times (8 + (7 + 6)))}{(3 \times (10 \times (9 + 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^4) + (8 \times (7 + 6)))}{(3 \times ((1 + 09) \times 5))} := \frac{((2 + (4 \times (8 + 7))) \times 6)}{((3 + (10 \times 9)) \times 5)} := \frac{((2 + (4 \times (8 - 7))) \times 6)}{(3 \times (1 - (0 - (9 + 5))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(2 - (4 - ((8 + 7) \times 6)))}{((3 + (10 + 9)) \times 5)} := \frac{(2 - (4 - ((8 - 7) \times 6)))}{((3 \times (1 \times (0 \times 9))) + 5)} := \frac{(2 - (4 - (8 + (7 \times 6))))}{((3 - (1 \times (0 - 9))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (((4 \times 8) + 7) \times 6))}{((3 + 10) \times (9 \times 5))} := \frac{(2 \times (((4 + 8) \times 7) - 6))}{(((3 \times 10) + 9) \times 5)} := \frac{(2 \times ((4 \times (8 + 7)) + 6))}{(3 \times (10 + (9 \times 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((4 + (8 + 7)) \times 6))}{(3 \times (1 \times (0 + 95)))} := \frac{(2 \times ((4 + (8 - 7)) \times 6))}{((3 \times 10) + (9 \times 5))} := \frac{(2 \times (4 - (8 - 76)))}{(2 \times (4 - (8 - 76)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (4 \times (8 + (7 - 6))))}{((3 - (1 - 0)) \times (9 \times 5))} := \frac{(2 \times (4 \times (8 - 7)^6))}{((3 - (1^{09})) \times 5)} := \frac{(2 \times (4 + ((8 - 7) \times 6)))}{((3 \times (1 + 09)) - 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (4 + (8 + (7 \times 6))))}{(3 \times (1 \times (0 + (9 \times 5))))} := \frac{(2^{4 \times (8-7)^6})}{((3 + (1^{09})) \times 5)} := \frac{(2 + (((4 \times 8) - 7) \times 6))}{((3 - (1 - 0)) \times 95)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + ((4 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6))}{((3 \times (10 \times 9)) + 5)} := \frac{(2 + (4 + ((8 - 7) \times 6)))}{(3 \times (1 - (0 - (9 - 5))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{71460}{89325} := \frac{(((7 + 1) \times 4)^6 + 0)}{((8^9) \times (3 + (2 + 5)))} := \frac{((7 - (1^4)) \times (6 - 0))}{(8 + (9 + (3 + 25)))} := \frac{((7 - (1^4)) \times 60)}{((89 + (3 - 2)) \times 5)}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((7 - (1^4))^6 + 0)}{(8 \times ((9^3) \times (2 \times 5)))} := \frac{((7 - (1 - 4)) \times (6 - 0))}{((8 \times (9 + (3 - 2))) - 5)} := \frac{((7 - (1 - 4)) \times 60)}{(((8 \times 9) + 3) \times (2 \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 \times (1 \times 4)) + 60)}{((8 + (9 + (3 + 2))) \times 5)} := \frac{((7 \times 14) - (6 - 0))}{((8 + (9 + (3 \times 2))) \times 5)} := \frac{((7 \times 14) + (6 - 0))}{((8 + (9 + (3^2))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 + (1^4)) \times (6 - 0))}{((8 + (9 - (3 + 2))) \times 5)} := \frac{((7 + (1^4)) \times 60)}{(8 \times ((9 + (3 \times 2)) \times 5))} := \frac{((7 + (1 + 4)) \times 60)}{(893 + (2 + 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 + (1 + 4))^6 + 0)}{(((8 \times 9)^3) \times (2 \times 5))} := \frac{((7 + (1 - 4)) \times (6 - 0))}{(8 + (9 + (3 + (2 \times 5))))} := \frac{((7 + 1) \times (4 \times (6 - 0)))}{(8 \times (9 + (3 \times (2 + 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 + 1) \times (4 \times 60))}{(8 \times ((9 + 3) \times 25))} := \frac{((7 + 1) \times (4 + (6 - 0)))}{((8 + ((9 - 3) \times 2)) \times 5)} := \frac{((7 + 1) \times (4 + 60))}{((8 + (9 + 3)) \times (2^5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 - 1) \times (4 \times 60))}{(8 \times (9 \times ((3 + 2) \times 5)))} := \frac{((7 - 1) \times (4 + 60))}{(8 \times ((9 - 3) \times (2 \times 5)))} := \frac{(7 - ((1^4) - (6 - 0)))}{(8 + (((9 - 3) \times 2) - 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 - (1 - (4 - (6 - 0))))}{(8 - (9 - (3 - (2 - 5))))} := \frac{(7 - (1 - (4 + (6 - 0))))}{(8 - (9 - (3 \times (2 + 5))))} := \frac{(7 - (1 - (46 - 0)))}{(((8 + (9 \times 3)) \times 2) - 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 - (1 + (4 - (6 - 0))))}{(8 + (9 + (3 - (2 \times 5))))} := \frac{(7 \times ((1^4) \times 60))}{(((8 \times 9) + 3) \times (2 + 5))} := \frac{(7 \times (1 \times (4 + 60)))}{(8 \times ((9 + (3 + 2)) \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + ((1^4) + 60))}{((8 + (9 \times (3 - 2))) \times 5)} := \frac{(7 + (1 - (4 - 60)))}{(8 \times (9 + ((3 - 2)^5))} := \frac{(7 + (1 + (4 \times (6 - 0))))}{(8 \times (9 + (3 - (2 + 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (1 + (4 \times 60)))}{((8 + (9 \times (3 \times 2))) \times 5)} := \frac{(7 + (1 + (4 + 60)))}{((8 + (9 + (3 - 2))) \times 5)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{76248}{95310} := \frac{(((7 - (6 - 2))^4) \times 8)}{((9^{5-3}) \times 10)} := \frac{(((7 \times (6 - 2)) - 4) \times 8)}{((9 + (5 \times 3)) \times 10)} := \frac{(((7 \times 6) + (2 + 4)) \times 8)}{(((9 \times 5) + 3) \times 10)}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((7 + (6^2)) \times 4) + 8)}{(9 \times (5^{3-1+0}))} := \frac{(((7 + (6 - 2)) \times 4) + 8)}{(95 - (3 \times 10))} := \frac{(((7 + 62) \times 4) + 8)}{(9 \times 5) + 310)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((76 - 2) \times 4) + 8)}{(95 \times (3 + (1 - 0)))} := \frac{(((7 - (6 - (2 \times 4))) \times 8)}{(9 \times (5 \times (3 - (1 - 0))))} := \frac{(((7 - (6 - (2^4))) \times 8)}{(9 + (5 + 3)) \times 10)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((7 - (6 \times (2 - 4))) \times 8)}{(95 \times (3 - (1 - 0)))} := \frac{(((7 - (6^2)) \times (4 - 8))}{((9 \times (5 \times 3)) + 10)} := \frac{(((7 - (6 - 2)) \times (4 \times 8))}{((9 - 5) \times (3 \times 10))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((7 - (6 - 2)) \times 48)}{(9 \times (5 \times (3 + (1 - 0))))} := \frac{(((7 \times (6 - (2 + 4))) + 8)}{(9 + (5 - (3 + (1 - 0))))} := \frac{(((7 \times (6 - (2 - 4))) + 8)}{((9^{5-3}) - (1 - 0))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{((7 \times (6 + (2 - 4))) + 8)}{(9 + (5 + (31 - 0)))} := \frac{((7 \times (6 + (2 - 4))) - 8)}{(9 + ((5 \times 3) + (1 - 0)))} := \frac{((7 \times (6 - 2)) + (4 \times 8))}{((9 \times 5) + (3 \times 10))} \\
 & := \frac{((7 + (6 \times 2)) \times (4 + 8))}{(95 \times (3 \times (1 - 0)))} := \frac{((7 + (6 + (2 - 4))) \times 8)}{((9 + (5 - 3)) \times 10)} := \frac{((7 + 62) \times (4 + 8))}{(9 \times ((5^3) - 10))} \\
 & := \frac{((76 + (2^4)) \times 8)}{((95 - 3) \times 10)} := \frac{((7 - 62) \times (4 - 8))}{((95 \times 3) - 10)} := \frac{(7 \times ((6 + (2 \times 4)) \times 8))}{((95 + 3) \times 10)} \\
 & := \frac{(7 \times (6 - (2 + (4 - 8))))}{((9 - (5 - 3)) \times 10)} := \frac{(7 \times (6 \times ((2^4) - 8)))}{((9 + 5) \times (3 \times 10))} := \frac{(7 \times (6 \times (2 - (4 - 8))))}{(9 \times (5 + (3 \times 10)))} \\
 & := \frac{(7 \times (6 + (2 + (4 - 8))))}{(9 - (5 - (31 - 0)))} := \frac{(76 - (2 \times (4 \times 8)))}{((9 \times 5) - (3 \times 10))} := \frac{(76 + (2 \times (4 + 8)))}{((9 \times (5 \times 3)) - 10)} \\
 & := \frac{(76 + (24 + 8))}{(9 \times (5 \times (3 \times (1 - 0))))} := \frac{76 + 248}{95 + 310}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{76328}{95410}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(((7 + (6 + 3))^2) \times 8)}{(((9 - 5)^4) \times 10)} := \frac{(((7 + (6 - 3))^2) + 8)}{(9 \times (5 \times (4 - (1 - 0))))} := \frac{((7 - (6 - (3^2))) \times 8)}{((9 + (5 - 4)) \times 10)} \\
 & := \frac{((7 - (6 - 3)) \times (2 + 8))}{((9 \times 5) + (4 + (1 - 0)))} := \frac{((7 \times (6 \times 3)) + (2 + 8))}{((9 \times (5 \times 4)) - 10)} := \frac{((7 + ((6 \times 3) + 2)) \times 8)}{(9 \times ((5 \times 4) + 10))} \\
 & := \frac{((7 + ((6 - 3)^2)) \times 8)}{((9 - 5) \times (4 \times 10))} := \frac{((7 + (6 - (3 + 2))) \times 8)}{((9 - (5 - 4)) \times 10)} := \frac{((7 + (6 \times (3 + 2))) \times 8)}{((95 \times 4) - 10)} \\
 & := \frac{((7 + (6 + (3 \times 2))) \times 8)}{((9 \times (5 \times 4)) + 10)} := \frac{((7 + (6 + (3 + 2))) \times 8)}{(9 \times (5 \times (4 \times (1 - 0))))} := \frac{((7 + (6 + 3)) \times 28)}{((9 + 5) \times (4 \times 10))} \\
 & := \frac{((7 + (63 \times 2)) \times 8)}{(95 \times (4 + 10))} := \frac{((7 + 6) \times (32 - 8))}{((95 \times 4) + 10)} := \frac{((7 - 6) \times ((3^2) \times 8))}{(9 \times (5 + (4 + (1 - 0))))} \\
 & := \frac{((7 - 6) \times 328)}{(((9 \times 5) - 4) \times 10)} := \frac{((76 \times (3 + 2)) + 8)}{((9 \times 54) - (1 - 0))} := \frac{((76 + (3 + 2)) \times 8)}{(9 \times ((5 + 4) \times 10))} \\
 & := \frac{(7 - (6 - (3 + 28)))}{((9 \times 5) - (4 + (1 - 0)))} := \frac{(7 - (6 + (3 - (2 + 8))))}{(9 - (5 + (4 - 10)))} := \frac{(7 \times (((6 - 3)^2) \times 8))}{(9 \times (5 \times (4 + 10)))} \\
 & := \frac{(7 \times ((6 - (3 + 2)) \times 8))}{((9 + 5) \times (4 + (1 - 0)))} := \frac{(7 \times ((6 + (3 - 2)) \times 8))}{(((9 \times 5) + 4) \times 10)} := \frac{(7 + (((6 - 3)^2) + 8))}{(9 + ((5 \times 4) + (1 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(7 + (6 - ((3^2) - 8)))}{(((9 - 5) \times 4) - (1 - 0))} := \frac{(7 + (6 - (3 - (2 - 8))))}{((9 \times 5) - (4 \times 10))} := \frac{(7 + (6 - (3 + (2 - 8))))}{(9 + (5 - (4 - 10)))} \\
 & := \frac{(7 + (6 + (3 + 28)))}{(9 + (5 + (41 - 0)))} := \frac{(76 - ((3 - 2) \times 8))}{((9 \times 5) + (4 \times 10))} := \frac{(76 - (32 + 8))}{(9 - (5 - (41 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(76 \times (32 + 8))}{(95 \times (4 \times 10))} := \frac{(76 + 328)}{(95 + 410)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{7629}{381450}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(((7 + 6) \times 2) + 9)}{((3 + (8 \times (1 \times 4))) \times 50)} := \frac{(((7 + 6) \times 2) - 9)}{(((3 \times (8 - 1)) - 4) \times 50)} := \frac{(((7 - 6)^2) \times 9)}{((3 - (8 - 14)) \times 50)} \\
 & := \frac{(((7 - 6)^2)^9)}{(3 - (8 - (1 + (4 + 50))))} := \frac{((7 - (6 - 2)) \times 9)}{(3 \times ((8 + (1^4)) \times 50))} := \frac{((7 - (6 - 2))^9)}{((3^{8+1^4}) \times 50)} \\
 & := \frac{((7 \times (6^2)) - 9)}{((3^{8+1-4}) \times 50)} := \frac{((7 \times (6 - 2)) + 9)}{((38 - (1^4)) \times 50)} := \frac{((7 + (6 - 2)) \times 9)}{((3 + (8 \times 1)) \times 450)} \\
 & := \frac{((7 + 6) \times 29)}{((381 - 4) \times 50)} := \frac{((7 - 6) \times (2^9))}{(((3 \times 8) + 1) \times (4^5 + 0))} := \frac{((7 - 6) \times (2 + 9))}{((3 + (8 \times (1^4))) \times 50)} \\
 & := \frac{((7 - 6) \times 29)}{(((3 \times 8) + (1 + 4)) \times 50)} := \frac{(7 - ((6 \times 2) - 9))}{((3 + (8 - 1)) \times (4 \times (5 - 0)))} := \frac{(7 - (6 - (2 \times 9)))}{(38 \times ((1 + 4) \times (5 - 0)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(7 - (6 - (2 + 9)))}{((3 + (8 + (1^4))) \times 50)} & := \frac{(7 - (6 + (2 - 9)))}{((3 + (8 + (1 - 4))) \times 50)} & := \frac{(7 \times ((6 \times 2) - 9))}{(3 \times ((8 - (1^4)) \times 50))} \\
 & := \frac{(7 \times ((6^2) - 9))}{(3 \times ((8 - 1) \times 450))} & := \frac{(7 \times (6 \times (2 \times 9)))}{((3 + 81) \times 450)} & := \frac{(7 + ((6 \times 2) + 9))}{(((3 \times (8 \times 1)) + 4) \times 50)} \\
 & := \frac{(7 + ((6 \times 2) - 9))}{((3 + (8 - (1^4))) \times 50)} & := \frac{(7 + ((6^2) + 9))}{((38 + 14) \times 50)} & := \frac{(7 + ((6^2) - 9))}{((38 - (1 \times 4)) \times 50)} \\
 & := \frac{(7 + ((6 - 2) \times 9))}{((3 + (8 \times (1 + 4))) \times 50)} & := \frac{(7 + (6 - (2 + 9)))}{(((3 \times (8 \times 1)) - 4) \times (5 - 0))} & := \frac{(7 + (6 - (2 - 9)))}{(((3 \times (8 \times 1)) - 4) \times 50)} \\
 & := \frac{(7 + (6 \times (2 \times 9)))}{((3 + (8 \times 14)) \times 50)} & := \frac{(7 + (6 + (2 \times 9)))}{((3 + ((8 - 1) \times 4)) \times 50)} & := \frac{(7 + (6 + (2 + 9)))}{(3 \times (8 \times ((1^4) \times 50)))} \\
 & := \frac{(7 + (6 + (2 - 9)))}{((3 + (8 - (1 + 4))) \times 50)} & := \frac{(7 + (6 + 29))}{((38 + (1 \times 4)) \times 50)} &
 \end{aligned}$$

3.32 33 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14586}{72930} & := \frac{((1 - (4 - (5 + 8))) \times 6)}{(7 + (293 - 0))} & := \frac{((1^4) \times ((5^8) + 6))}{(((7 - 2)^9) + 30)} & := \frac{((1^4) \times ((5^8) - 6))}{(((7 - 2)^9) - 30)} \\
 & := \frac{((1^4) \times (5 \times (8 \times 6)))}{(((7^2) - 9) \times 30)} & := \frac{((1^4) \times (5^{8-6}))}{(((7 \times 2) - 9)^3 + 0)} & := \frac{((1^4) \times (58 \times 6))}{(((7^2) + 9) \times 30)} \\
 & := \frac{((1 + (4 + (5 \times 8))) \times 6)}{((7 - 2) \times (9 \times 30))} & := \frac{((1 + (4 + (5 + 8))) \times 6)}{((7 + (2 + 9)) \times 30)} & := \frac{((1 + (4 + 58)) \times 6)}{((72 - 9) \times 30)} \\
 & := \frac{((1 + 4) \times ((5^8) \times 6))}{(((7 - 2)^9) \times 30)} & := \frac{((1 - 4) \times (5 - (8 \times 6)))}{((72 \times 9) - (3 - 0))} & := \frac{((1 - 4) \times (5 - (8 + 6)))}{((7 - 2) \times (9 \times (3 - 0)))} & \& := \frac{(1 - ((4 - (5 + 8)) \times 6))}{(7 - (2 - (9 \times 30)))} & := \frac{(1 - ((4 - (5 + 8)) \times 6))}{(7 + (2 + 9))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (4 - (5 + (8 - 6))))}{((7 \times 2) + (9 - (3 - 0)))} & := \frac{(1 - (4 + (5 - (8 + 6))))}{(7 + (2 - (9 - 30)))} & := \frac{(1 \times (4 \times (5 - (8 - 6))))}{(72 - (9 + (3 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (4 \times (5 \times (8 - 6))))}{((7 \times 29) - (3 - 0))} & := \frac{(1 \times (4 + (5 - (8 - 6))))}{((7 \times 2) - (9 - 30))} & := \frac{(1 \times (4 + (5 \times (8 - 6))))}{((7^2) - (9 - 30))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (4 + (5 + (8 - 6))))}{(7 + ((2 \times 9) + 30))} & := \frac{(1 \times (45 + (8 \times 6)))}{((7 - 2) \times (93 - 0))} & := \frac{(1 + (4 - (5 - (8 - 6))))}{((7^2) - (9 + 30))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (4 + ((5 \times 8) - 6)))}{((7 - 2) \times (9 + 30))} & := \frac{(1 + (4 + (5 - (8 - 6))))}{(7 + ((2 + 9) \times (3 - 0)))} & := \frac{(1 + (4 + (5 \times (8 - 6))))}{((7 + (2 \times 9)) \times (3 - 0))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (4 + (5^{8-6})))}{(((7 \times 2) - 9) \times 30)} & := \frac{(1 + (4 + (5 + (8 + 6))))}{(((7^2) - 9) \times (3 - 0))} & := \frac{(14 + (5 - (8 - 6)))}{(7 + (2 \times (9 + 30)))} \\
 & := \frac{(14 + (5 \times (8 + 6)))}{((7 - (2 - 9)) \times 30)} & := \frac{(14 + (5 + (8 + 6)))}{(72 + (93 - 0))} & := \frac{(14 + (5 + (8 - 6)))}{(7 \times ((2 \times 9) - (3 - 0)))} \\
 \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18279}{30465} & := \frac{(((1 + 8)^2) + 7) \times 9}{(30 \times (4 \times (6 + 5)))} & := \frac{(((1^{8^2}) + 7) \times 9)}{(30 \times (4 \times (6 - 5)))} & := \frac{(((1^8) + 2) \times (7 \times 9))}{(304 + (6 + 5))} \\
 & := \frac{((1 - (8 - (2 + 7))) \times 9)}{(3 \times (0 - ((4 - 6) \times 5)))} & := \frac{((1^8) + ((2 \times 7) + 9))}{(30 - ((4 - 6) \times 5))} & := \frac{((1^8) + ((2 \times 7) - 9))}{(3 + (0 - (4 - (6 + 5))))} \\
 & := \frac{((1^8) + ((2^7) - 9))}{((30 + (4 + 6)) \times 5)} & := \frac{((1 + ((8 \times 2) + 7)) \times 9)}{(3 \times (0 + (4 \times (6 \times 5))))} & := \frac{((1 + ((8^2) - 7)) \times 9)}{(30 \times ((4 \times 6) + 5))} \\
 & := \frac{((1 + (8 - (2 - 7))) \times 9)}{(3 - (0 - 4)) \times (6 \times 5)} & := \frac{((1 + (8 + (2 + 7))) \times 9)}{((30 + (4 \times 6)) \times 5)} & := \frac{((1 + 8) \times (27 \times 9))}{((3^{0 \times 4 + 6}) \times 5)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - ((8 + 2) \times (7 - 9)))}{(3 + ((0 - (4 - 6))^5))} & := \frac{(1 - (8 + (2 - (7 \times 9))))}{(((3 \times (0 + 4)) + 6) \times 5)} & := \frac{(1 \times ((8 - (2 - 7)) \times 9))}{(3 \times ((0 \times 4) + 65))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((8 \times (2 + 7)) + 9))}{((3 - (0 - (4 \times 6))) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 \times ((8 \times 27) + 9))}{(((3^{04}) - 6) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 \times ((8^2) - (7 + 9)))}{((3^{04}) - (6 - 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((8 - 2) \times (7 \times 9)))}{(((30 \times 4) + 6) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 \times ((8 - 2) \times (7 + 9)))}{((30 - (4 - 6)) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 \times (8 - ((2 \times 7) - 9)))}{((3 \times (0 \times 46)) + 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 + (2 - (7 - 9))))}{(30 + ((4 - 6) \times 5))} := \frac{(1 \times (82 - (7 - 9)))}{((30 + (4 - 6)) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 + ((8 \times 2) + (7 - 9)))}{((3 + (0 - (4 - 6))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (8 - (2 + (7 - 9))))}{(3 \times (0 + (4 + (6 - 5))))} := \frac{(1 + (8 \times (2 - (7 - 9))))}{((30 \times 4) - 65)} := \frac{(1 + (8 + (2 + (7 + 9))))}{(3 \times (0 + (4 + (6 + 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (8 + (2 + 79)))}{(3 \times (0 + ((4 + 6) \times 5)))} := \frac{(1 + (827 + 9))}{(3 \times (0 + 465))} := \frac{(18 \times ((2 \times 7) + 9))}{(3 \times (0 + (46 \times 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(18 \times (2 + 79))}{((3^{04}) \times (6 \times 5))} := \frac{(18 + (27 \times 9))}{(((3^{04}) + 6) \times 5)} := \frac{(18 + 279)}{(30 + 465)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{18654}{93270}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((1^8) + 6) \times 5) - 4}{((9 \times 3) + (2^7 + 0))} := \frac{(((1 + 8) \times 6) - 5) \times 4}{((9 + (3 + 2)) \times 70)} := \frac{((1^{86}) + (5 \times 4))}{((9 + (3 \times 2)) \times (7 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1^8) + ((6 + 5) \times 4))}{(9 + (3 \times (2 + 70)))} := \frac{((1 + (8 + 6)) \times (5 + 4))}{(9 \times (3 + (2 + 70)))} := \frac{((1 + 8) \times 654)}{(9 \times 3270)} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 - 8) \times (6 - 54))}{((9 + 3) \times (2 \times 70))} := \frac{((18 - 6) \times 54)}{((9 + 3) \times 270)} := \frac{(1 - (8 - (6 + (5 \times 4))))}{((9 \times 3) - (2 - 70))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (8 - (65 - 4)))}{(9 \times (3 + (27 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 \times ((8 - (6 - 5)) \times 4))}{(9 + (3 + (2^7 + 0)))} := \frac{(1 \times ((8 + 6) \times (5 + 4)))}{(9 \times ((3 - 2) \times 70))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((8 + 6) \times 54))}{(9 \times (3 \times (2 \times 70)))} := \frac{(1 \times ((8 - 6) \times (5 + 4)))}{(9 + (3 \times (27 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 \times ((86 - 5) \times 4))}{((9 - 3) \times 270)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 - (6 \times (5 - 4))))}{(9 + ((3 - 2)^7 + 0))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 - (6 - 54)))}{((9 - (3 + 2)) \times 70)} := \frac{(1 \times (8 + ((6 \times 5) + 4)))}{((9 - (3 \times 2)) \times 70)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 + (6 - (5 + 4))))}{(9 + ((3^2) + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 + (6 \times (5 - 4))))}{(9 - ((3^2) - 70))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 + (6 + (5 + 4))))}{((9 \times (3 + 2)) + 70)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (86 + 54))}{((9 + (3 - 2)) \times 70)} := \frac{(1^{8654})}{(((9 - 3) \times 2) - (7 - 0))} := \frac{(1 + ((8 + 65) \times 4))}{(((9^3) \times 2) + (7 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (8 - (6 - (5 - 4))))}{(9 - (3 - (2 \times (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 + (8 - (6 \times (5 - 4))))}{(9 - (3 - (2 + (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 + (8 \times ((6 - 5) \times 4)))}{(93 + (2 + 70))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (8 + (6 \times (5 + 4))))}{(9 \times ((3 + 2) \times (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + (8 + (6 + (5 \times 4))))}{(((9 \times 3) - 2) \times (7 - 0))} := \frac{(1 + (8 + (6 + (5 + 4))))}{(93 + (27 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (8 + (6 + (5 - 4))))}{(9 + (3 - (2 - 70)))} := \frac{(18 - ((6 - 5)^4))}{(9 + ((3 \times 2) + 70))} := \frac{(186 - (5 - 4))}{(932 - (7 - 0))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{23715}{94860}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (3 + (7 \times 1))) + 5)}{(((9 - 4) \times 8) + 60)} := \frac{((2 \times (3 + 71)) + 5)}{((94 + 8) \times (6 - 0))} := \frac{((2 + (3 \times 71)) \times 5)}{((9 - 4) \times 860)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + (3 + (7 \times 1))) \times 5)}{((9 - 4) \times (8 \times (6 - 0)))} := \frac{((2 + (37 \times 1)) \times 5)}{((9 - (4 - 8)) \times 60)} := \frac{((23 - (7 - 1)) \times 5)}{((9 - 4) \times (8 + 60))} \\
 &:= \frac{((23 \times (7 \times 1)) - 5)}{((9 + 4) \times (8 \times (6 - 0)))} := \frac{((23 \times 7) + (1^5))}{(9 \times (4 + (8 + 60)))} := \frac{(2 - (3 - (7 \times (1^5))))}{((9 \times (4 - 8)) + 60)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (3 - (7 + (1 - 5))))}{(94 - (86 - 0))} := \frac{(2 - (3 - (7 + 15)))}{((9 \times 4) + (8 \times (6 - 0)))} := \frac{(2 - (3 - (71 + 5)))}{((9 + (4 - 8)) \times 60)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (3 \times (7 - 15)))}{((9 \times 4) + (8 + 60))} := \frac{(2 \times (3 - (7 - 15)))}{((9 \times 4) - (8 - 60))} := \frac{(2 \times (3 \times (7 - (1^5))))}{(9 \times (4^{8-6+0}))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (3 \times (7 - (1 - 5))))}{(((9 \times 4) + 8) \times (6 - 0))} := \frac{(2 \times (3 \times (7 \times (1 + 5))))}{(948 + 60)} := \frac{(2 \times (3 \times (7 \times (1^5))))}{((9 \times (4 + 8)) + 60)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (3 + (7 - (1^5))))}{(9 \times (4 \times (8 - (6 - 0))))} := \frac{(2 \times (3 + (7 \times (1^5))))}{(94 - (8 + (6 - 0)))} := \frac{(2 + ((3 + (7 + 1)) \times 5))}{((9 \times (4 \times 8)) - 60)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (3 \times (7 \times (1^5))))}{(94 - (8 - (6 - 0)))} := \frac{(2 + (3 \times (7 + (1 + 5))))}{(((9 + 4) \times 8) + 60)} := \frac{(2 + (3 + ((7 + 1) \times 5)))}{(94 + (86 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (3 + (7 - (1^5))))}{(((9 + 4) \times 8) - 60)} := \frac{(2 + (3 + (7 \times (1 + 5))))}{(94 \times (8 - (6 - 0)))} := \frac{(2 + (3 + (7 \times (1^5))))}{((9 \times (4 + 8)) - 60)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (3 + (7 + 15)))}{(94 + (8 + (6 - 0)))} := \frac{(2 + (37 \times (1 + 5)))}{((9 \times 4) + 860)} := \frac{(2 + (37 - 15))}{(94 + (8 - (6 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(237 \times (1 + 5))}{(948 \times (6 - 0))} := \frac{(237 + (1 + 5))}{(9 \times (48 + 60))} := \frac{(237 - 15)}{(948 - 60)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{24716}{30895}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((2^{4 \times 7} \times 1) \times 6))}{(3 \times (0 + ((8^9) \times 5)))} := \frac{((2 \times (4 + (7 \times 1))) + 6)}{(3 - (0 - (8 \times (9 - 5))))} := \frac{((2 \times (4 + 71)) + 6)}{((30 \times 8) - (9 \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^4) \times ((7 + 1) \times 6))}{(30 \times (8 \times (9 - 5)))} := \frac{((2^4) \times (7 + 16))}{((3 - (0 - 89)) \times 5)} := \frac{((2 + (4 \times (7 + 1))) \times 6)}{(3 \times (0 + ((8 + 9) \times 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + (4 + (7 - 1))) \times 6)}{(3 + (0 - (8 - 95)))} := \frac{((2 + (47 + 1)) \times 6)}{((3 - (0 - (8 \times 9))) \times 5)} := \frac{(2 - ((4 - 71) \times 6))}{((30 \times (8 + 9)) - 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (4 - (7 - (1^6))))}{((3 \times (0 \times 89)) + 5)} := \frac{(2 \times ((4 \times (7 + 1)) + 6))}{((3 \times (0 \times 8)) + 95)} := \frac{(2 \times ((4 \times (7 + 1)) - 6))}{((30 - (8 + 9)) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((4 \times (7 - 1)) + 6))}{(((3 \times (0 + 8)) - 9) \times 5)} := \frac{(2 \times ((4 + (7 \times 1)) \times 6))}{(((3 \times (0 + 8)) + 9) \times 5)} := \frac{(2 \times (4 \times ((7 - 1) \times 6)))}{(30 \times (8 + (9 - 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (4 \times (7 - (1^6))))}{((3 - ((0 \times 8) - 9)) \times 5)} := \frac{(2 \times (4 \times (7 - (1 - 6))))}{(30 \times (8 - (9 - 5)))} := \frac{(2 \times (4 \times (7 \times (1^6))))}{(3 - (0 - ((8 \times 9) - 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (4 \times (7 + (1^6))))}{(3 - (0 - ((8 \times 9) + 5)))} := \frac{(2 \times (4 \times (7 + (1 - 6))))}{((3 + (0 - (8 - 9))) \times 5)} := \frac{(2 \times (4 + ((7 - 1) \times 6))}{((3 - (0 - (8 + 9))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (4 + (7 - (1^6))))}{(3 - (0 - (8 + (9 + 5))))} := \frac{(2 \times (4 + (7 - (1 - 6))))}{(3 + (0 - (8 - (9 \times 5))))} := \frac{(2 \times (4 + (7 \times (1 \times 6))))}{(3 - (0 - (8 \times (9 + 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (4 + (7 + (1 + 6))))}{((3 \times (0 \times 8)) + (9 \times 5))} := \frac{(2 \times (47 + (1 + 6)))}{(3 \times ((0 \times 8) + (9 \times 5)))} := \frac{(2 + (4 + (7 - (1^6))))}{(3 - (0 - (8 + (9 - 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(24 \times (7 + (1 \times 6)))}{((3 - (0 - (8 - 9))) \times 5)} := \frac{(24 \times ((7 - 1) \times 6))}{(3 \times (0 + (8 \times (9 \times 5))))} := \frac{(24 \times (7 \times 16))}{(30 \times (8 \times (9 + 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(24 \times (7 + (1 \times 6)))}{(30 + (8 \times (9 \times 5)))} := \frac{(24 \times (71 + 6))}{(30 \times ((8 \times 9) + 5))} := \frac{24 + 716}{30 + 895}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{49380}{61725}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((4 \times 9) - 3) \times (8 - 0))}{(6 \times (1 + ((7^2) + 5)))} := \frac{((4 \times (9 \times 3)) - 80)}{((6 + (17^2)) \times 5)} := \frac{((4 \times (9 + 3)) - (8 - 0))}{(6 + (1 \times ((7^2) - 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times (9 - 3)) + (8 - 0))}{((6 + ((1^7) \times 2)) \times 5)} := \frac{((4 \times (9 - 3)) + 80)}{((6 + (1 \times 7)) \times (2 \times 5))} := \frac{((4 \times 9) - (3 \times (8 - 0)))}{(6 - (1 - (7 - (2 - 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times 93) - 80)}{((6 - (1 - (72 \times 5))))} := \frac{((4 + (9 \times 3)) \times (8 - 0))}{((4 + (9 \times 3)) \times (8 - 0))} := \frac{((4 + (9 + 3)) \times (8 - 0))}{((4 + (9 + 3)) \times (8 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 + 9) \times (3 \times (8 - 0)))}{((6 + (1 \times 72)) \times 5)} := \frac{((61 \times (7 - 2)) + 5)}{((49 + 3) \times (8 - 0))} := \frac{((6 - (1^7)) \times (2^5))}{(4 - (9 + (3 - 80)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times ((9 \times 3) - (8 - 0)))}{((6 + (1 \times 72)) \times 5)} := \frac{(((6 \times 17) + 2) \times 5)}{(((6 \times 17) + 2) \times 5)} := \frac{(6 \times (1 + (7 + (2 + 5))))}{(6 \times (1 + (7 + (2 + 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times ((9 \times 3) - (8 - 0)))}{((6 - (1 - (7 \times 2))) \times 5)} := \frac{(4 \times ((9 \times 3) + (8 - 0)))}{((6 + (1^7)) \times 25)} := \frac{(4 \times ((9 + 3) \times (8 - 0)))}{(4 \times ((9 + 3) \times (8 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times ((9 - 3) \times (8 - 0)))}{(6 \times (1 + (7 + (2^5))))} := \frac{(4 \times (9 - (3 - (8 - 0))))}{((6 - (1 - (7 + 2))) \times 5)} := \frac{(4 \times (9 - (3 - 80)))}{((61 \times 7) - (2 - 5))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (9 \times (3 \times (8 - 0))))}{((6^{17+2}) \times 5)} := \frac{(4 \times (9 \times (3^8 + 0)))}{((6 - 1) \times ((7 + 2)^5))} := \frac{(4 \times (9 + (3 - (8 - 0))))}{(6 + (1 \times (7 + (2 + 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (9 + (3 \times (8 - 0))))}{(((6 - 1) \times 7) - 2) \times 5} := \frac{(4 \times (9 + (3 + (8 - 0))))}{((6 + (1 \times (7 \times 2))) \times 5)} := \frac{(4 \times (9 + (38 - 0)))}{((61 - (7 \times 2)) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (93 - 80))}{((6 \times (1 + (7 + 2))) + 5)} := \frac{(4 + ((9 + 3) \times (8 - 0)))}{(6 + (17 \times (2 + 5)))} := \frac{(4 + (9 \times (3 \times (8 - 0))))}{((6 + (1 \times (7^2))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (9 + (3 - (8 - 0))))}{(6 + (1 \times (7 + (2 - 5))))} := \frac{(4 + (9 + (3 + (8 - 0))))}{(6 - (1 + (7 - (2^5))))} := \frac{(4 + (9 + (3 + 80)))}{(6 \times (1 + ((7 \times 2) + 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(49 \times (3 \times (8 - 0)))}{(6 \times (1 \times ((7^2) \times 5)))} := \frac{(49 + (3 - (8 - 0)))}{(6 + (1 \times (7 \times (2 + 5))))} := \frac{(49 + (3 + (8 - 0)))}{(6 - (1 - (7 \times (2 \times 5))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{49708}{62135}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((4 \times 9) - (7 - 0)) \times 8)}{((62 - (1 + 3)) \times 5)} := \frac{(((4 \times 9) + 70) \times 8)}{((6^2) + ((1 + 3)^5))} := \frac{((4 - (9 - (7 - 0)))^8)}{(((6 - (2 \times 1))^3) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times (9 \times (7 - 0))) - 8)}{(62 + (1 \times (3^5)))} := \frac{((4 \times (9 + (7 - 0))) + 8)}{(6 \times ((2 + (1^3)) \times 5))} := \frac{((4 \times (9 + (7 - 0))) - 8)}{(6 + (2^{13+5}))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times (9 + 70)) + 8)}{((6 + 21) \times (3 \times 5))} := \frac{((4 \times (9 + 70)) - 8)}{(((6 \times 2) - 1) \times 35)} := \frac{((4 \times 9) - (7 \times (0 - 8)))}{(((6^2) - 13) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times 970) + 8)}{((6^2) \times 135)} := \frac{((4^{9-7+0}) \times 8)}{((6 + (2 \times 13)) \times 5)} := \frac{((4^{9-7+0}) + 8)}{((4^{9-7+0}) + 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 + (9 - (7 - 0))) \times 8)}{(6 \times (2 + (1 \times (3 + 5))))} := \frac{((4 + (9 + (7 - 0))) \times 8)}{(((6^2) + (1 + 3)) \times 5)} := \frac{((49 - (7 - 0)) \times 8)}{(6 \times (2 \times (1 \times 35)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - 97) \times (0 - 8)}{(62 \times (1 \times (3 \times 5)))} := \frac{(4 - ((9 - 70) \times 8))}{(((6 \times 21) - 3) \times 5)} := \frac{(4 - (9 \times (7 \times (0 \times 8))))}{(6 + (2 - (1 - (3 - 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times ((9 - (7 - 0))^8))}{(((6 - 2) \times (1 + 3)) \times 5)} := \frac{(4 \times (9 - (7 - (0 \times 8))))}{(6 + (2 - (1 \times (3 - 5))))} := \frac{(4 \times (9 - (7 \times (0 \times 8))))}{((6 + (2 + (1^3))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (9 - (7 \times (0 - 8))))}{((62 + (1 \times 3)) \times 5)} := \frac{(4 \times (9 - (7 + (0 - 8))))}{((6 + (2 - (1 - 3))) \times 5)} := \frac{(4 \times (9 \times (7 - (0 \times 8))))}{((6 + (2 + 1)) \times 35)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (9 + (7 - (0 \times 8))))}{(62 + (13 + 5))} := \frac{(4 \times (9 + (7 - (0 - 8))))}{(6 \times (2 + (13 + 5)))} := \frac{(4 \times (9 + (7 + (0 - 8))))}{(6 - (2 - (1 + 35)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (97 - (0 - 8)))}{(((6^2) - 1) \times (3 \times 5))} := \frac{(4^{9-7+0 \times 8})}{(6 - (2 \times (1 - (3 + 5))))} := \frac{(4 + ((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 8))}{(((6^{2 \times 1}) - 3) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (9 + (7 - (0 \times 8))))}{((6 - (2 - (1^3))) \times 5)} := \frac{(4 + (9 + (7 - (0 - 8))))}{((6 + (2 - (1^3))) \times 5)} := \frac{(4 + (9 + (7 + (0 - 8))))}{(6 + (2 - (1 - (3 + 5))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{63140}{78925}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((6 \times 3) - 1) \times 40)}{((78 + 92) \times 5)} := \frac{((6 - (3 \times 1)) \times 40)}{((7 + (8 - 9)) \times 25)} := \frac{((6 - (3 + 1)) \times 40)}{((7 \times (8 + (9 - 2))) - 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 - (3 - 1)) \times (4 - 0))}{((7 + (8 - (9 + 2))) \times 5)} := \frac{((6 - (3 - 1)) \times 40)}{((7 - (8 - 9)) \times 25)} := \frac{((6 \times (3 + 1)) - (4 - 0))}{((7 + ((8 - 9) \times 2)) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 \times (3 + 1)) + (4 - 0))}{(7 \times ((8 - (9 - 2)) \times 5))} := \frac{((6 \times (3 + 1)) + 40)}{((7 - (8 - 9)) \times (2 \times 5))} := \frac{((6 \times (3 - 1)) + 40)}{(78 - ((9 \times 2) - 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6^3 \times 1) - (4 - 0))}{(((7 + 8) \times (9 \times 2)) - 5)} := \frac{((6^3 \times 1) + (4 - 0))}{(((7 + 8) \times (9 \times 2)) + 5)} := \frac{((6^3 \times 1) + 40)}{(((7 - (8 - 9))^2) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((6^{3+1}) + (4 - 0))}{(((7 \times 8) + 9) \times 25)} := \frac{((6^{3-1}) - (4 - 0))}{(7 - (8 - (9 + (2^5))))} := \frac{((6^{3-1}) \times (4 - 0))}{(7 + ((89 \times 2) - 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6^{3-1}) + (4 - 0))}{(7 + (8 + ((9 - 2) \times 5)))} := \frac{((6^3) \times (1 + (4 - 0)))}{((7 + 8) \times (9 \times (2 \times 5)))} := \frac{((6^3) + 140)}{((78 + (9 + 2)) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 - 3) \times 140)}{(7 \times ((8 + (9 - 2)) \times 5))} := \frac{(6 - (3 - (1^4 + 0)))}{(7 - (8 - (9 + (2 - 5))))} := \frac{(6 - (3 - (1 + 40)))}{(7 + (8 \times (9 + (2 - 5))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(6 \times ((3-1) \times 40))}{((7+(8+9)) \times 25)} &:= \frac{(6 \times (3-(1^4+0)))}{(7-(8+(9-25)))} &:= \frac{(6 \times (3-(1-40)))}{((7+(8 \times (9-2))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (3 \times (1 \times (4-0))))}{(7+((8 \times (9+2))-5))} &:= \frac{(6 \times (3+(1^4+0)))}{((7-(8-(9-2))) \times 5)} &:= \frac{(6^{3-1^4+0})}{((7-((8-9) \times 2)) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(6+(3-(1^4+0)))}{(7+((8-9) \times (2-5)))} &:= \frac{(6+(3-(1-40)))}{((7+(8-9)) \times (2 \times 5))} &:= \frac{(6+(314-0))}{((7-(8-(9^2))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(63+(1-(4-0)))}{(7-(8-((9^2)-5)))} &:= \frac{(63+(1+(4-0)))}{(7-(8-((9^2)+5)))} &:= \frac{(63+(1+40))}{((7+(8+(9+2))) \times 5)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{3729}{186450}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((3 \times 7)^2) - 9)}{(1 \times (8 \times (6 \times 450)))} &:= \frac{(((3+7) \times 2) - 9)}{((1+(8+(6-4))) \times 50)} &:= \frac{(((3+7)^2) - 9)}{((1+(86+4)) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((3-7) \times 2) + 9)}{((1^{864}) \times 50)} &:= \frac{((3 \times (7 \times 2)) - 9)}{((1+(8+(6 \times 4))) \times 50)} &:= \frac{((3 \times (7+2)) + 9)}{((3 \times (7+2)) + 9)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (7+2)) - 9)}{(1 \times ((8+(6+4)) \times 50))} &:= \frac{((3 \times (7-2)) + 9)}{((1^8) \times (6 \times (4 \times 50)))} &:= \frac{((3 \times (7-2)) - 9)}{(1 \times ((8-(6-4)) \times 50))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times 7) - (2+9))}{((3 \times 7) - (2+9))} &:= \frac{((3 \times 7) + (2+9))}{((3 \times 7) + (2+9))} &:= \frac{((3 \times 7) + 29)}{((3 \times 7) + 29)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3+(7-2)) \times 9)}{(1 \times ((8+(6-4)) \times 50))} &:= \frac{((3+7) \times (2 \times 9))}{(1 \times ((8+(6 \times 4)) \times 50))} &:= \frac{((37 \times 2) + 9)}{(((1+8) \times 6) - 4) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{((37 \times 2) - 9)}{(1 \times ((8+64) \times 50))} &:= \frac{(3-(7-(2+9)))}{(18 \times ((6+4) \times 50))} &:= \frac{(3-(7 \times (2-9)))}{((1+(86-4)) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{((1+(8^{6-4})) \times 50)}{((1+(8-(6-4))) \times 50)} &:= \frac{((1+(8-(6-4))) \times 50)}{((1+(8-(6-4))) \times 50)} &:= \frac{(1 \times (((8 \times 6) + 4) \times 50))}{(3-(7 \times (2-9)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3-(7+(2-9)))}{((1-(8-(6+4))) \times 50)} &:= \frac{(3-(7-29))}{(((1^8) + (6 \times 4)) \times 50)} &:= \frac{(3 \times ((7-2) \times 9))}{((1+(8+6)) \times 450)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (7-(2-9)))}{((18+(6 \times 4)) \times 50)} &:= \frac{(3 \times (7+(2+9)))}{(3 \times (7+(2+9)))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (7+29))}{(3 \times (7+29))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3+((7 \times 2) + 9))}{(3+((7 \times 2) + 9))} &:= \frac{(3+((7 \times 2) - 9))}{(3+((7 \times 2) - 9))} &:= \frac{(3+((7-2) \times 9))}{((18-6) \times 450)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1+(8+((6^4)-(5-0))))}{(3+(7-(2-9)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 \times ((6+4) \times (5-0))))}{(3+(7 \times (2 \times 9)))} &:= \frac{(18-6) \times (4 \times 50))}{(3+(7 \times (2+9)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1+(8 \times (6-4))) \times 50)}{(3+(7+(2 \times 9)))} &:= \frac{((1^8) \times 6450)}{(37-(2 \times 9))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 \times ((6+4) \times 50)))}{(37-(2-9))} \\
 &:= \frac{((18+(6+4)) \times 50)}{((18+(6+4)) \times 50)} &:= \frac{((1+(8+(6+4))) \times 50)}{((1+(8+(6+4))) \times 50)} &:= \frac{(1 \times (((8 \times 6) - 4) \times 50))}{(1 \times (((8 \times 6) - 4) \times 50))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{7356}{102984}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((7+3) \times 5) + 6)}{(1 \times (0 + (2 \times (98 \times 4))))} &:= \frac{(((7-3) \times 5) + 6)}{(((10^2) - 9) \times (8-4))} &:= \frac{(((7-3)^5) \times 6)}{((10+(2+9)) \times (8^4))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7-(3-5)) \times 6)}{((1^{02}) \times (9 \times 84))} &:= \frac{((7 \times (3+5)) + 6)}{(((10^2) + 9) \times 8) - 4)} &:= \frac{((7 \times (3+5)) - 6)}{(10 \times (2 + ((9+8) \times 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 \times 3) - (5-6))}{(((10+29) \times 8) - 4)} &:= \frac{((7 \times 3) + (5-6))}{((7 \times 3) + (5-6))} &:= \frac{((7+(3-5)) \times 6)}{((7+(3-5)) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7+3) \times 56)}{((10+(2 \times (98 \times 4)))} &:= \frac{((7-3) \times (5+6))}{((1 \times (0 - ((2-(9 \times 8)) \times 4)))} &:= \frac{((7-3) \times 56)}{(10 \times (2 \times (9+(8+4))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7-(3-(5 \times 6)))}{(7-(3-(5 \times 6)))} &:= \frac{((7-3) \times (5+6))}{((10+(2 \times (9 \times 8))) \times 4)} &:= \frac{((7-3) \times 56)}{((10-2) \times (98 \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{((102+(9+8)) \times 4)}{(7-(3 \times (5-6)))} &:= \frac{(10+((2 \times 98) + 4))}{(7-(3-(5+6)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (0+(2 \times (9+(8+4))))}{(7-(3-(5-6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1-(0-(2 \times (9+8)))) \times 4)}{(7 \times ((3 \times 5) + 6))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (0+(2+((9+8) \times 4))))}{(7 \times ((3+5) \times 6))} &:= \frac{(((1^{02}) + 9) \times 84)}{(7 \times (3-(5-6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10+((2^9) \times (8-4)))}{(7 \times (3+(5-6)))} &:= \frac{(10+2) \times (98 \times 4)}{(10+2) \times (98 \times 4)} &:= \frac{((1^{02}) \times (98 \times 4))}{((1^{02}) \times (98 \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10+(2 \times (9+84)))}{(10+(2 \times (9+84)))} &:= \frac{(7+((3 \times 5) - 6))}{(1 \times (0 - ((2-9) \times (8 \times 4))))} &:= \frac{(7+((3^5) + 6))}{(1 \times (0 - ((2^9) - (8^4))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(7 + ((3 + 5) \times 6))}{(10 \times (2 - (9 - 84)))} &:= \frac{(7 + (3 \times (5 - 6)))}{(1 + (0 - (29 - 84)))} &:= \frac{(7 + (3 + (5 + 6)))}{(1 \times (0 + (298 - 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (3 + (5 - 6)))}{(10 + (29 \times (8 - 4)))} &:= \frac{(7 + (3 + 56))}{(1 \times (0 + ((2 + 9) \times 84)))} &:= \frac{(7 + (35 + 6))}{((1 + (0 - (2 - 9))) \times 84)} \\
 &:= \frac{(73 + (5 + 6))}{((1 - (0 - 2)) \times (98 \times 4))} &:= \frac{(73 + (5 - 6))}{((1 - (0 - (2 + 9))) \times 84)} &:= \frac{(73 - 56)}{(10 + ((29 \times 8) - 4))}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.33 34 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{12073}{96584} &:= \frac{(((1^2 + 0) + 7)^3)}{((9 - ((6 - 5)^8))^4)} &:= \frac{((1^{207}) + 3)}{(9 + (6 + (5 + (8 + 4))))} &:= \frac{((1 + (2 - (0 - 7))) \times 3)}{((9 + (6 + 5)) \times (8 + 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (2^{07})) \times 3)}{(9 \times ((6 \times 58) - 4))} &:= \frac{((1 + (2 - 0)) \times 73)}{((9 - 6) \times 584)} &:= \frac{((1 + (20 + 7)) \times 3)}{((9 - (6 - 5)) \times 84)} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + 207) \times 3)}{(96 \times ((5 + 8) \times 4))} &:= \frac{((12 \times (0 + 7)) + 3)}{((9 - 6) \times (58 \times 4))} &:= \frac{((12 + (0 - 7)) \times 3)}{((9 + (6 - 5)) \times (8 + 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (2 \times (0 - (7 - 3))))}{((9 + (6 - (5 - 8))) \times 4)} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((2^{07})^3))}{(((9 - (6 - 5)) \times 8)^4)} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((2^{07}) + 3))}{(((9 \times (6 \times 5)) - 8) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (2 - ((0 \times 7) - 3)))}{(9 - (6 - (5 + (8 \times 4))))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (2 - (0 - (7 + 3))))}{((9 - (6 - 5)) \times (8 + 4))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (2 - (0 - (7 - 3))))}{((9 + (6 + (5 - 8))) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (2 - (0 \times 73)))}{(9 + (6 + (5 - (8 - 4))))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (2 \times (0 + (7 - 3))))}{((9 - (6 - (5 + 8))) \times 4)} &:= \frac{(1 \times (20 - (7 + 3)))}{((9 + (6 + 5)) \times (8 - 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (20 \times (7 - 3)))}{(9 + (6 + (5^{8-4})))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (20 + (7 \times 3)))}{((9 + (65 + 8)) \times 4)} &:= \frac{(1 \times (207 + 3))}{((9 + (6 + 5)) \times 84)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (207 - 3))}{(96 \times (5 + (8 + 4)))} &:= \frac{(1^{2073})}{(9 + (6 + (5 - (8 + 4))))} &:= \frac{(1 + ((2 - (0 - 7)) \times 3))}{((96 - (5 \times 8)) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + ((20 - 7) \times 3))}{((9 + (6 - 5)) \times (8 \times 4))} &:= \frac{(1 + (2 - (0 - (7 + 3))))}{(1 + (2 - (0 - (7 + 3))))} &:= \frac{(1 + (2 - (0 - (7 - 3))))}{((9 + (6 + 5)) \times (8 + 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (2 - (0 \times 73)))}{(9 + (6 + (5 + (8 - 4))))} &:= \frac{(1 + (20 + (7^3)))}{((96 - 5) \times (8 \times 4))} &:= \frac{(12 - (0 - (7 \times 3)))}{((9 + (65 - 8)) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(12 - (0 - 73))}{(96 + 584)} &:= \frac{(12 \times ((0 \times 7) + 3))}{(9 \times ((6 - 5) \times (8 \times 4)))} &:= \frac{(120 - (7 \times 3))}{(9 \times (((6 \times 5) - 8) \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(120 - 73)}{(((9 \times 6) + (5 \times 8)) \times 4)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17469}{58230} &:= \frac{(((1^7) + 4)^6) \times 9}{((5^{8-2}) \times 30)} &:= \frac{(((1 + 7) \times 4) + 6) \times 9}{(((5 \times 8) - 2) \times 30)} &:= \frac{(((1 + 7) \times 4) - 6) \times 9}{((5 + 8) \times (2 \times 30))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((1^7) + (4 + 6)) \times 9)}{((5 + (8 - 2)) \times 30)} &:= \frac{(((1 + (7 - 4)) \times 6) + 9)}{((5 \times (8 \times 2)) + 30)} &:= \frac{(((1 - 7) \times (4 - 6)) - 9)}{(5 \times (8 - (2 \times (3 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((17 - 4) \times 6) + 9)}{((5 \times (8^2)) - 30)} &:= \frac{((1 - (7 \times (4 - 6))) \times 9)}{((5 + (8 + 2)) \times 30)} &:= \frac{((1 - (7 + 4)) \times (6 - 9))}{((5 \times 8) + (2 \times 30))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1^{74}) \times 69)}{(5 \times ((8 \times 2) + 30))} &:= \frac{((1^7) - (4 - (6 \times 9)))}{(5 \times ((8^2) - 30))} &:= \frac{((1 + (7 \times (4 \times 6))) \times 9)}{(((5 + 8)^2) \times 30)} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (7 + (4 \times 6))) \times 9)}{(5 \times ((8^2) \times (3 - 0)))} &:= \frac{((1 + (7 - 4)) \times 69)}{(5 \times (8 \times (23 - 0)))} &:= \frac{((1 + (74 - 6)) \times 9)}{((5 + (8^2)) \times 30)} \\
 &:= \frac{((17 + (4 \times 6)) \times 9)}{(5 \times (82 \times (3 - 0)))} &:= \frac{((17 - 4) \times 69)}{(5 + 8) \times 230} &:= \frac{(1 - ((7 \times (4 - 6)) - 9))}{(5 \times (8 + (2^3 + 0)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(1 - (7 - (4 \times (6 + 9))))}{(5 \times (8 - (2 - 30)))} := \frac{(1 - (7 - (4 \times 69)))}{(5 \times ((8 - 2) \times 30))} := \frac{(1 - (7 \times (4 - (6 + 9))))}{(5 \times (82 - 30))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((74 + 6) \times 9))}{(5 \times (8 \times (2 \times 30)))} := \frac{(1 \times (7 - (4 - (6 + 9))))}{((5 \times (8 - 2)) + 30)} := \frac{(1 \times (7 - (4 + (6 - 9))))}{(5 - (8 - (23 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (7 - (4 - 69)))}{(5 \times (8 \times (2 \times (3 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 \times (7 \times ((4 \times 6) - 9)))}{((5 \times (8^2)) + 30)} := \frac{(1 + (7 + (4 - (6 - 9))))}{((5 \times (8 \times 2)) - 30)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (7 + (4 + (6 + 9))))}{(5 + (82 + (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + (7 + (4 + (6 - 9))))}{(58 + (2 - 30))} := \frac{(1 + (7 + (4 + 69)))}{((5 \times 8) + 230)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (7 + (46 - 9)))}{(5 \times ((8 + 2) \times (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + (74 - (6 \times 9)))}{(5 \times (8 + (2 \times (3 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 + (74 - (6 + 9)))}{(5 \times (8 + (2 + 30)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(174 + (6 + 9))}{((5 + (8 \times 2)) \times 30)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{31842}{79605}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((3 \times 18) + 4) \times 2)}{((7 - (9 - 60)) \times 5)} := \frac{(((3 \times 18) - 4) \times 2)}{(7 + ((9 - (6 - 0))^5))} := \frac{((3 \times (1 \times (8 \times 4))) - 2)}{((7 - (9 \times 6)) \times (0 - 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (1 \times (8 + 4))) - 2)}{(79 + (6 - (0 \times 5)))} := \frac{((3 \times (18 - 4)) + 2)}{((7 + (9 + (6 - 0))) \times 5)} := \frac{((3 \times (18 - 4)) - 2)}{((7 \times (9 + (6 - 0))) - 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times 18) + (4 - 2))}{(7 \times (9 + (6 - (0 - 5))))} := \frac{((3 + (1 + (8 + 4))) \times 2)}{(79 + (6 + (0 - 5)))} := \frac{((3 + 1) \times (8 \times 42))}{(7 \times (96 \times (0 + 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 - 1) \times (8^{4 \times 2}))}{(((7 + 9)^6 + 0) \times 5)} := \frac{((31 \times (8 - 4)) - 2)}{((7 + (9 \times (6 - 0))) \times 5)} := \frac{((31 \times 8) - 42)}{((7 + (96 - 0)) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((31 + 8) \times 42)}{(7 \times (9 \times (60 + 5)))} := \frac{((31 - 8) \times (4 + 2))}{(((7 \times 9) + (6 - 0)) \times 5)} := \frac{((31 - 8) \times 42)}{(7 \times ((9 + 60) \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (1 - ((8 + 4)^2)))}{((79 - (6 - 0)) \times 5)} := \frac{(3 - (1 - (8 - (4 - 2))))}{((7 - (9 - (6 - 0))) \times 5)} := \frac{(3 - (1 - (8 + (4 + 2))))}{((7 - (9 + 6)) \times (0 - 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (1 - (84 \times 2)))}{((79 + (6 - 0)) \times 5)} := \frac{(3 - (1^{842}))}{(7 + (9 - (6 - (0 - 5))))} := \frac{(3 - (1 + (8 - 42)))}{(79 + (6 - (0 - 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (((1 + 8) \times 4) + 2))}{(((7 \times 9) - (6 - 0)) \times 5)} := \frac{(3 \times ((18 \times 4) - 2))}{(7 \times ((9 + (6 - 0)) \times 5))} := \frac{(3 \times (1 \times (8 - 4) \times 2))}{((7 - 9) \times (6 \times (0 - 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (1 \times (8^{4-2})))}{((7 + 9) \times (6 \times (0 + 5)))} := \frac{(3 \times (1 \times (8 + (4 + 2))))}{(7 \times (9 + (6 - (0 \times 5))))} := \frac{(3 \times (1 \times (84 - 2)))}{(((7 \times 9) + 60) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (1 - (8 - 42)))}{((79 - 60) \times 5)} := \frac{(3 + (1^{842}))}{(7 + (9 - (6 - (0 \times 5))))} := \frac{(3 + (1 + (8 - (4 + 2))))}{(7 + (9 - (6 + (0 - 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (1 + (8 \times (4 - 2))))}{((7 + (9 - (6 - 0))) \times 5)} := \frac{(3 + (1 + (8 + (4^2))))}{(7 \times (9 + (6 + (0 - 5))))} := \frac{3184 + 2}{7960 + 5} \\
 &:= \frac{3184 - 2}{7960 - 5}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{53298}{71064}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((5 \times (3 \times 2)) + 9) \times 8)}{((7 \times (10 \times 6)) - 4)} := \frac{(((5 \times (3^2)) - 9) \times 8)}{((7 - (1 - 0)) \times 64)} := \frac{(((5 + 3) \times 2) + (9 + 8))}{((7 + (10 - 6)) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((5 + 3)^2) + (9 + 8))}{((7 \times (10 + 6)) - 4)} := \frac{((5 \times (3 + 2)) - (9 - 8))}{(7 + (1 - (0 - (6 \times 4))))} := \frac{((5^3) - (2 - (9 \times 8)))}{((71 + (0 - 6)) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{((5^3) + (2 - (9 - 8)))}{(7 \times (1 \times (0 + (6 \times 4))))} := \frac{((5^3) + (2 + (9 + 8)))}{((7 + (1 - 0)) \times (6 \times 4))} := \frac{((5 + ((3 - 2)^9)) \times 8)}{((7 + (1 - 0))^{6-4})} \\
 &:= \frac{((53 - (2 + 9)) \times 8)}{(7 \times (1 \times (0 + 64)))} := \frac{((53 \times 2) - (9 - 8))}{(7 \times (10 \times (6 - 4)))} := \frac{((53 - 29) \times 8)}{(((7 \times 10) - 6) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 - ((3 - (2 + 9)) \times 8))}{((7 + (10 + 6)) \times 4)} := \frac{(5 - ((3 \times (2 - 9)) + 8))}{((7 - (1^{06})) \times 4)} := \frac{(5 - ((3 - 29) \times 8))}{(71 \times ((0 \times 6) + 4))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(5 - (3 - ((2 \times 9) - 8)))}{(7 - (1 + (0 - (6 + 4))))} := \frac{(5 - (3 - (2 - (9 - 8))))}{(7 - (1 - (0 - (6 - 4))))} := \frac{(5 - (3 - (2 \times (9 + 8))))}{((7 - (1 + (0 - 6))) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 - (3 - (2 + (9 + 8))))}{(7 \times ((1^{06}) \times 4))} := \frac{(5 - (3 - (29 + 8)))}{((7 - (1 \times (0 - 6))) \times 4)} := \frac{(5 \times (3 \times (2 \times (9 - 8))))}{(((7 - (1 - 0)) \times 6) + 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times (3^{2 \times (9-8)}))}{((7 \times 10) - (6 + 4))} := \frac{(5 + ((3 \times (2 \times 9)) - 8))}{((7 \times 10) - (6 - 4))} := \frac{(5 + ((3 \times 29) - 8))}{(7 \times ((10 - 6) \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (3 - (2 \times (9 - 8))))}{(7 + (1 - (0 \times 64)))} := \frac{(5 + (3 + (2 - (9 - 8))))}{(7 + ((1^{06}) + 4))} := \frac{(5 + (3 + (2 \times (9 + 8))))}{((7 + (1 - (0 - 6))) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (3 + (2 + (9 + 8))))}{((7 - (1 - 0))^{6-4})} := \frac{(5 + (3 + (2 + 98)))}{((7 - (1 - 0)) \times (6 \times 4))} := \frac{(5 + (3 + 298))}{((7 + 10) \times (6 \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (32 + (9 + 8)))}{(7 + (1 - (0 - 64)))} := \frac{(53 + ((2 \times 9) - 8))}{(7 \times (10 + (6 - 4)))} := \frac{(53 + (2 \times (9 + 8)))}{((7 \times (10 + 6)) + 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(532 - (9 - 8))}{(710 - (6 - 4))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{5371}{429680} := \frac{(((5 + 3) \times 7) + 1)}{((42 + (9 + 6)) \times 80)} := \frac{(((5 - 3) \times 7) - 1)}{(((4^2) - (9 - 6)) \times 80)} := \frac{((5 \times (3 \times 7)) - 1)}{(((4 \times 2) + 96) \times 80)}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((5 \times (3 + 7)) + 1)}{((4 + ((2^9) - 6)) \times (8 - 0))} := \frac{((5 \times 3) - (7 + 1))}{((4 + ((2 + 9) \times 6)) \times (8 - 0))} := \frac{((5 \times 3)^{7-1})}{(((4 + (2 + 9))^6) \times 80)} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 \times 3) + (7 - 1))}{((4 + (2 + (9 + 6))) \times 80)} := \frac{((5^3) + (7 \times 1))}{((4 + (2 \times 9)) \times (6 \times 80))} := \frac{((5^3) + 71)}{((4 + (2 \times 96)) \times 80)} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 + 3) \times (7 \times 1))}{((4 - (2 - (9 \times 6))) \times 80)} := \frac{((5 + 3) \times (7 - 1))}{(4 \times (((2 \times 9) - 6) \times 80))} := \frac{((5 - 3) \times (7 - 1))}{((4 + (2^{9-6})) \times 80)} \\
 &:= \frac{((53 \times 7) + 1)}{(((42 \times 9) - 6) \times 80)} := \frac{(5 - (3 - (7 \times 1)))}{((4 + (2 + (9 - 6))) \times 80)} := \frac{(5 - (3 - (7 + 1)))}{(4 \times ((2 \times 96) + (8 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 - (3 - (7 - 1)))}{(((4 - 2)^{9-6}) \times 80)} := \frac{(5 \times ((3 \times 7) + 1))}{((4 + (2 + (9 - 6))) \times 80)} := \frac{(5 \times (3 \times (7 + 1)))}{(4 \times (2 \times ((9 + 6) \times 80)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times (3 \times (7 - 1)))}{((4 + (2 + 9)) \times (6 \times 80))} := \frac{(5 \times (3 + (7 \times 1)))}{(((4 \times 29) - 6) \times 80)} := \frac{(5 \times (3 + (7 - 1)))}{((42 + (9 - 6)) \times 80)} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + ((3 \times 7) + 1))}{((4 + (29 - 6)) \times 80)} := \frac{(5 + ((3 \times 7) - 1))}{((4 \times (2^9)) - (6 \times (8 - 0)))} := \frac{(5 + (3 - (7 \times 1)))}{(4 \times (2 - (9 \times (6 - (8 - 0)))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (3 - (7 - 1)))}{(4 \times ((2 + (9 - 6)) \times (8 - 0)))} := \frac{(5 + (3 \times (7 \times 1)))}{((4 \times ((2^9) + 6)) + (8 - 0))} := \frac{(5 + (3 \times (7 + 1)))}{(4 \times ((2^9) + (68 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (3 \times (7 - 1)))}{(((4 \times 2) + (9 + 6)) \times 80)} := \frac{((4^2) + 9) \times (6 \times (8 - 0))}{(5 + (3 + (7 \times 1)))} := \frac{((4 + ((2 \times 9) - 6)) \times 80)}{(5 + (3 + (7 + 1)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (3 + (7 - 1)))}{(4 \times ((29 + 6) \times (8 - 0)))} := \frac{(((4^2) - 9) \times (6 \times 80))}{(5 + (37 \times 1))} := \frac{(53 - (7 \times 1))}{((4 - ((2 - 9) \times 6)) \times 80)} \\
 &:= \frac{(53 + (7 \times 1))}{((4 + (2 + (9 \times 6))) \times 80)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{5832}{174960} := \frac{(((5 \times 8) - 3) \times 2)}{(1 \times (((7 \times 4) + 9) \times 60))} := \frac{(((5 + 8) \times 3) - 2)}{(1 \times (74 \times (9 + (6 - 0))))} := \frac{((5 \times (8 \times 3)) - 2)}{(((17 \times 4) - 9) \times 60)}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((5 \times (8 - 3)) + 2)}{(1 + (749 + 60))} := \frac{((5 \times (8 - 3)) - 2)}{(1 + (749 - 60))} := \frac{((5 \times 8) - (3 \times 2))}{(17 \times (4 \times (9 + (6 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 \times 8) + (3 \times 2))}{((((1 + 7) \times 4) - 9) \times 60)} := \frac{((5 \times 8) + 32)}{((1 - (7 \times (4 - 9))) \times 60)} := \frac{((5 + (8 + 3)) \times 2)}{((1^{74}) \times 960)} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 + (8 - 3)) \times 2)}{(((1^{74}) + 9) \times 60)} := \frac{((5 + (8 - 3))^2)}{(((1^7) + 49) \times 60)} := \frac{(5 + 8) \times 32}{((17 - 4) \times 960)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(5 - (8 - (3 \times 2)))}{(1 - (7 - ((4 \times 9) + 60)))} &:= \frac{(5 - (8 - (3^2)))}{((1 + (7 + (4 - 9))) \times 60)} &:= \frac{(5 - (8 - (3 + 2)))}{((1^{749}) \times 60)} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times ((8 \times 3) + 2))}{(1 \times ((74 - 9) \times 60))} &:= \frac{(5 \times (8 - (3 \times 2)))}{(((1^7) + 49) \times (6 - 0))} &:= \frac{(5 \times (8 \times (3 \times 2)))}{((1 + 74) \times (96 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times (8 \times (3 - 2)))}{(1 \times ((7 + (4 + 9)) \times 60))} &:= \frac{(5 \times (8 + 32))}{((1 + ((7 + 4) \times 9)) \times 60)} &:= \frac{(5^{8 \times (3-2)})}{((((1^7) + 4)^9) \times (6 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (8 - (3 \times 2)))}{(1 - (7 - (4 \times (9 \times (6 - 0))))))} &:= \frac{(5 + (8 - (3^2)))}{(1 \times ((7 + (4 - 9)) \times 60))} &:= \frac{(5 + (8 - (3 + 2)))}{((17 - (4 + 9)) \times 60)} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (8 - (3 - 2)))}{((((1^7) - (4 - 9)) \times 60)} &:= \frac{(5 + (8 \times (3 - 2)))}{(1 \times ((74 - 9) \times (6 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(5 + (8 + (3^2)))}{(1 \times ((74 \times 9) - (6 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (8 + (3 + 2)))}{((1^{74}) \times (9 \times 60))} &:= \frac{(5 + (8 + (3 - 2)))}{(1 \times (7 \times (4 \times (9 + (6 - 0))))))} &:= \frac{(5 + (83 + 2))}{((((1^7) + 4) \times (9 \times 60))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (83 - 2))}{((1 - (7 - 49)) \times 60)} &:= \frac{(58 - (3 \times 2))}{((174 \times 9) - (6 - 0))} &:= \frac{(58 \times (3^2))}{((1 + (7 \times 4)) \times (9 \times 60))} \\
 &:= \frac{(58 - 32)}{((1 + (7 - (4 - 9))) \times 60)}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.34 35 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10542}{36897} &:= \frac{(((1 - (0 - 5))^4) \times 2)}{(3 \times (6 \times (8 \times (9 \times 7))))} &:= \frac{((1 - (0 - (5 \times 4))) \times 2)}{(3 + (6 \times (8 + (9 + 7))))} &:= \frac{((1 - (0 - (5 + 4))) \times 2)}{((3 + (6 - (8 - 9))) \times 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 - (0 - 54)) \times 2)}{(3 \times ((6 + 8) \times 9) + 7)} &:= \frac{((1^{05}) \times (4^2))}{((3 + (6 + (8 - 9))) \times 7)} &:= \frac{((1^{05}) \times (4 + 2))}{(3 - (6 - (8 + (9 + 7))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((10 \times 5) - (4^2))}{(((3 \times 6) + (8 - 9)) \times 7)} &:= \frac{((10^{5+4}) \times 2)}{(((3 \times 6) - 8)^9) \times 7)} &:= \frac{((10 + (5 \times 4)) \times 2)}{(3 \times (6 + (8^{9-7})))} \\
 &:= \frac{((10 + 5) \times (4 \times 2))}{((3 + ((6 \times 8) + 9)) \times 7)} &:= \frac{((10 + 54) \times 2)}{((36 - 8) \times (9 + 7))} &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 - (4 - 2))))}{((3 \times (6 - (8 - 9))) - 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (5^{4-2})))}{(3 + (6 + (89 - 7)))} &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 + (4 \times 2))))}{(3 + ((6 \times 8) - (9 - 7)))} &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 + (4 - 2))))}{((3 \times (6 - (8 - 9))) + 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 + 42)))}{(3 + (68 + 97))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((5 + 4) \times 2))}{(3 + (6 \times (8 + (9 - 7))))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (5 \times (4 + 2))))}{(3 + (6 + (89 + 7)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (5 \times (4 - 2))))}{(3 - ((6 - 8) \times (9 + 7)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (5 \times 42)))}{((3 + (6 \times (8 + 9))) \times 7)} &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (54 - 2)))}{((3 + (6 + (8 + 9))) \times 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (5 - (4^2))))}{(3 \times (6 - (8 - (9 + 7))))} &:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (5 - (4 + 2))))}{(3 - (6 - (8 + (9 - 7))))} &:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (5 - 42)))}{((36 - (8 + 9)) \times 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 \times ((5 + 4) \times 2))}{(((3 \times 6) + (8 \times 9)) \times 7)} &:= \frac{(10 \times (5^{4 \times 2}))}{(((3 - (6 - 8))^9) \times 7)} &:= \frac{(10 \times (5^{4-2}))}{((36 + 89) \times 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 \times (5 + (4 - 2)))}{((36 + (8 - 9)) \times 7)} &:= \frac{(10 \times (54 \times 2))}{(36 \times (8 + 97))} &:= \frac{(10 + ((5 \times 4) + 2))}{(3 + ((6 \times (8 + 9)) + 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 + ((5 + 4) \times 2))}{(3 + (6 - (8 - 97)))} &:= \frac{(10 + (5 \times (4^2)))}{((3 - (6 - 8)) \times (9 \times 7))} &:= \frac{(10 + (54 + 2))}{(3 \times (6 + (8 + (9 \times 7))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1054 + 2)}{(3689 + 7)} &:= \frac{(1054 - 2)}{(3689 - 7)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\blacktriangleright \frac{12307}{98456} := \frac{(((1 + 2)^3 + 0) \times 7)}{(9 \times ((8 + (4 \times 5)) \times 6))} := \frac{((1 - (2 - (3 - 0))) \times 7)}{(98 + ((4 \times 5) - 6))} := \frac{((1 - (2 + 3)) \times (0 - 7))}{((9 - 8) \times (4 \times 56))}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((1^2) \times (30 + 7))}{((9 \times 8) + (4 \times 56))} &:= \frac{((1^2) + (3 - (0 \times 7)))}{(9 + (8 + (4 + (5 + 6))))} &:= \frac{((1 + (2^3 + 0)) \times 7)}{(((98 + 4) \times 5) - 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (2^3 + 0))^7)}{(9 \times (8 \times ((4 + 5)^6)))} &:= \frac{((1 + 2) \times (30 + 7))}{((98 \times (4 + 5)) + 6)} &:= \frac{((1 + 2) \times (30 - 7))}{(((9 \times 8) + (4 \times 5)) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + 2)^{3+0 \times 7})}{(9 \times (8 \times (4 + (5 - 6))))} &:= \frac{((12 \times (3 - 0)) - 7)}{((9 \times (8 \times 4)) - 56)} &:= \frac{(1 - (2 - (3 - (0 \times 7))))}{(9 - (8 - (4 + (5 + 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (2 - (3 - (0 - 7))))}{(98 + (4 - (5 \times 6)))} &:= \frac{(1 - (2 \times (3 \times (0 - 7))))}{((9 \times (8 \times 4)) + 56)} &:= \frac{(1 - (2 + (3 + (0 - 7))))}{(9 + (8 - (4 - (5 + 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (2 - 307))}{(9 \times (8 \times (4 + (5 \times 6))))} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((2^3 + 0) \times 7))}{((98 \times 4) + 56)} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((2^3 + 0)^7))}{((9 + (8 + (4 - 5)))^6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((2^3 + 0) + 7))}{((9 - 8) \times (4 \times (5 \times 6)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((2 + (3 - 0)) \times 7))}{((9 - (8 - 4)) \times 56)} &:= \frac{(1 \times (2 - (3 + (0 - 7))))}{((9 + (8 - (4 + 5))) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (2 \times (3 \times (0 + 7))))}{((98 \times 4) - 56)} &:= \frac{(1 \times (2 \times (30 - 7)))}{(98 + (45 \times 6))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (2^{3+0 \times 7}))}{((9 - (8 + (4 - 5)))^6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (2 + (3 - (0 \times 7))))}{(9 - (8 - (45 - 6)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (2 + (3 - (0 - 7))))}{((9 + (8 + (4 - 5))) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(1 \times (2 + (30 + 7)))}{(((9 \times 8) - (4 \times 5)) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{1^{2307}}{(9 - (8 + (4 - (5 + 6))))} &:= \frac{(1 + ((2^3 + 0) \times 7))}{((9 - 8) \times 456)} &:= \frac{(1 + (2 - (3 \times (0 - 7))))}{((9 \times 8) + (4 \times (5 \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (2 - (3 + (0 - 7))))}{(9 + (8 + (45 - 6)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (2 + (3 - (0 - 7))))}{(9 + (84 + (5 + 6)))} &:= \frac{(12 \times (3 \times (0 + 7)))}{(9 \times ((8 - 4) \times 56))} \\
 &:= \frac{123 + 07}{984 + 56} &:= \frac{123 - 07}{984 - 56} &
 \end{aligned}$$

► **29684**
37105

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((2 + 9) \times 6) + 8) \times 4}{((3 + (71 - 0)) \times 5)} &:= \frac{(((2 \times (9 \times 6)) - 8) \times 4)}{((3 + 7) \times (10 \times 5))} &:= \frac{(((2 \times (9 + 6)) + 8) \times 4)}{((37 + (1 - 0)) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((2 \times 9) - 6) \times (8 + 4))}{((37 - (1 - 0)) \times 5)} &:= \frac{(((2 \times 9) - 6) \times (8 - 4))}{(3 + (7 + (10 \times 5)))} &:= \frac{(((2 + (9 \times 6)) \times 8) - 4)}{(37 \times (10 + 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((2 + (9 - 6)) \times 8)^4)}{((3 + (7 + 10))^5)} &:= \frac{((2 - (9 \times (6 - 8))) \times 4)}{((3 + (7 + 10)) \times 5)} &:= \frac{((2 \times ((9 - 6) \times 8)) - 4)}{((3 + (7 + (1 - 0))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (9 \times 6)) - (8 \times 4))}{(((3 + 7) \times 10) - 5)} &:= \frac{((2 \times (96 + 8)) - 4)}{(3 \times ((7 + 10) \times 5))} &:= \frac{((2 \times (96 - 8)) - 4)}{(3 \times (7 \times 10)) + 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times 96) - (8 - 4))}{((37 + 10) \times 5)} &:= \frac{((2 \times 96) - 84)}{((37 - 10) \times 5)} &:= \frac{((2^{9+6-8}) - 4)}{(((3 \times 7) + 10) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^{9-6}) - (8 - 4))}{(3 + (7 + (1 \times (0 - 5))))} &:= \frac{((2^{9-6}) \times (8 + 4))}{(3 \times ((7 + (1 - 0)) \times 5))} &:= \frac{((2^{9-6}) + (8 - 4))}{(3 + (7 - (1 \times (0 - 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - ((9 \times (6 - 8)) + 4))}{((3 - (7 \times 1)) \times (0 - 5))} &:= \frac{(2 - ((9 \times (6 - 8)) - 4))}{((3 - (7 - 10)) \times 5)} &:= \frac{(2 \times (((9 - 6) \times 8) - 4))}{((3 + (7 \times (1 - 0))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((9 - (6 - 8)) \times 4))}{(((3 \times 7) + (1 - 0)) \times 5)} &:= \frac{(2 \times ((9 \times 6) - (8 + 4)))}{(3 \times (7 \times (1 \times (0 + 5))))} &:= \frac{(2 \times ((9 + 6) \times (8 - 4)))}{((3 + 7) \times (10 + 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((9 - 6) \times (8 + 4)))}{(3 \times ((7 - (1 - 0)) \times 5))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (9 \times (6 - (8 - 4))))}{(3 + (7 \times (1 - (0 - 5))))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (9 \times (6 + (8 - 4))))}{(3 \times ((7 \times 10) + 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2^{9+6-8-4})}{(3 + (7 \times (1^{05})))} &:= \frac{(2 + (9 \times (6 - (8 - 4))))}{(3 + (7 + (10 + 5)))} &:= \frac{(2 + (9 \times (6 + (8 + 4))))}{((3 \times (7 \times 10)) - 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (9 \times (6 + (8 - 4))))}{(3 + (7 + 105))} &:= \frac{(296 - (8 - 4))}{((3 + (7 \times 10)) \times 5)} &:= \frac{(296 + (8 - 4))}{((37 \times 10) + 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{2968 + 4}{3710 + 5} &:= \frac{2968 - 4}{3710 - 5} &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{64732}{80915} &:= \frac{(((6 + (4 \times 7)) \times 3) + 2)}{(80 + ((9 + 1) \times 5))} := \frac{(((6 - 4)^7) \times (3 + 2))}{(80 \times (9 + (1^5)))} := \frac{((6 \times 4)^{7-3-2})}{(80 \times (9 \times (1^5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6^4) - 732)}{((80 \times 9) - 15)} := \frac{((6 + (4 + (7 - 3))) \times 2)}{((8 + ((0 \times 9) - 1)) \times 5)} := \frac{((6 + (47 - 3)) \times 2)}{(80 + (9 \times (1 \times 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 - 4) \times (7 + (3^2)))}{(8 \times (0 + (9 + (1 - 5))))} := \frac{((6 - 4) \times (73 \times 2))}{(((8 \times (0 + 9)) + 1) \times 5)} := \frac{((6 - 4)^{7+3-2})}{(8 \times (0 + ((9 - 1) \times 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((64 \times (7 + 3))^2)}{(80^{9-1-5})} := \frac{(6 - ((4 - (7^3)) \times 2))}{((80 + 91) \times 5)} := \frac{(6 - (4 + (7 - (3^2))))}{(8 + (0 - (9 - (1 + 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times ((4 \times (7 \times 3)) + 2))}{((80 \times (9 - 1)) + 5)} := \frac{(6 \times ((4 \times (7 - 3))^2))}{(80 \times (9 + 15))} := \frac{(6 \times ((4 \times 7) + (3 \times 2)))}{((8 - (0 - 9)) \times 15)} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times ((4 \times 7) + 32))}{((80 + (9 + 1)) \times 5)} := \frac{(6 \times ((4 + 7) \times (3 \times 2)))}{((8 - (0 - 91)) \times 5)} := \frac{(6 \times (4 - (7 - (3^2))))}{((8 - ((0 \times 9) - 1)) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (4 \times (7 + (3 + 2))))}{(8 \times (0 + (9 \times (1 \times 5))))} := \frac{(6 \times (4 \times (7 + (3 - 2))))}{(80 \times (9 - (1 + 5)))} := \frac{(6 \times (4^{7-3 \times 2}))}{(80 - ((9 + 1) \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (4^{7-3-2}))}{(8 \times (0 + (9 + (1 + 5))))} := \frac{(6 \times (4 + (7 - (3 - 2))))}{(((8 \times (0 + (9 + 1))) - 5)} := \frac{(6 \times (4 + (7 + (3 - 2))))}{(((8 - (0 - (9 + 1))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 + (((4 \times 7) + 3) \times 2))}{((8 - (0 - (9 \times 1))) \times 5)} := \frac{(6 + ((4 + (7 \times 3)) \times 2))}{(80 - (9 + (1^5)))} := \frac{(6 + (4 - (7 - (3^2))))}{((8 \times (0 \times 9)) + 15)} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 + (4 + (7 \times (3 \times 2))))}{(80 - (9 + (1 + 5)))} := \frac{(64 \times (7 + (3 \times 2)))}{(80 \times (9 - (1 - 5)))} := \frac{(64 \times (7 + (3 - 2)))}{(80 \times (9 - (1^5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(64^{7-3 \times 2})}{(8 \times (0 + (9 + (1^5))))} := \frac{64 + 7 + 3 + 2}{80 + 9 + 1 + 5} := \frac{(64 + 732)}{(80 + 915)} \\
 &:= \frac{647 + 3 + 2}{809 + 1 + 5} := \frac{647 + 3 - 2}{809 + 1^5}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{72836}{91045} &:= \frac{(((7 \times 2) + 8) \times 3) + 6)}{(9 \times (1 - (0 - (4 + 5))))} := \frac{(((7 \times 2) - 8) \times 3) - 6)}{(9 + ((1^{04}) + 5))} := \frac{(((7^2) + (8 - 3)) \times 6)}{(9 \times (1 \times (0 + 45)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((7 + 2) \times 8) + 36)}{(9 \times 10) + 45)} := \frac{(((7 - (2 - (8 - 3))) \times 6)}{((9 + (10 - 4)) \times 5)} := \frac{(((7 \times ((2 + 8) \times 3)) + 6)}{(9 \times (10 + (4 \times 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((7 \times (2 \times (8 + 3))) + 6)}{((9 + (1 - 0)) \times (4 \times 5))} := \frac{(((7 \times (2 + 8)) - (3 \times 6))}{((9 - (1 \times (0 - 4))) \times 5)} := \frac{(((7 \times (2 + 8)) + (3 \times 6))}{((9 \times 10) + (4 \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((7 \times 2) + ((8 + 3) \times 6))}{(91 - (0 - (4 + 5)))} := \frac{(((7 \times 2) + (8 + (3 \times 6)))}{((9 \times (1 - (0 - 4))) + 5)} := \frac{(((7 + (2 - (8 - 3))) \times 6)}{(9 + (1 - (0 - (4 \times 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((7 + (2 - 8)) \times 36)}{(9 \times ((1^{04}) \times 5))} := \frac{(((7 + 2) \times (8 \times (3 + 6)))}{(9 \times (10 \times (4 + 5)))} := \frac{(((7 + 2) \times (8 + 36))}{(9 \times (10 + 45))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((7 + 2) \times 836)}{(9 \times 1045))} := \frac{(((72 - (8 \times 3)) \times 6)}{((9 - (1 - 0)) \times 45)} := \frac{(((72 + 8) \times (3 \times 6))}{(9 \times (10 \times (4 \times 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 - (2 - (8 - (3 - 6))))}{((9 - (1 - (0 - 4))) \times 5)} := \frac{((7 \times ((2 \times (8 - 3)) - 6))}{(((9 + (1 - 0)) \times 4) - 5)} := \frac{((7 \times (2 \times ((8 \times 3) - 6)))}{(9 \times ((10 \times 4) - 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 \times (2 \times (8 + (3 \times 6))))}{(91 \times ((0 \times 4) + 5))} := \frac{((7 \times (2 + (8 + (3 \times 6))))}{((9 + (10 \times 4)) \times 5)} := \frac{((7 + (2 - (8 + (3 - 6))))}{(9 + ((1^{04}) - 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 + (2 + (8 - (3 + 6))))}{(9 + (1 - (0 \times 45)))} := \frac{((7 + (2 + (8 - (3 - 6))))}{((9 + (1 \times (0 - 4))) \times 5)} := \frac{((7 + (28 + (3^6))))}{(910 + 45)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 + (28 + (3 + 6))))}{(9 + (1 - (0 - 45)))} := \frac{((7 + (28 + (3 - 6))))}{((9 \times (1 - (0 - 4))) - 5)} := \frac{((7 + (283 - 6))}{((9 \times (10 \times 4)) - 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((72 + (8 \times (3 + 6))))}{(9 \times (1 \times (0 + (4 \times 5))))} := \frac{((72 + (8 \times (3 - 6))))}{((9 - (1 + (0 - 4))) \times 5)} := \frac{((72 + (8 \times 36))}{((9 + (1 - 0)) \times 45)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(728 \times (3 + 6))}{(910 \times (4 + 5))} \quad := \frac{(728 - 36)}{(910 - 45)}$$

► $\frac{73284}{91605} := \frac{(((7 + 3)^2) - (8 + 4))}{((9 + 1) \times (6 - (0 - 5)))} := \frac{(((73 + 2) \times 8) + 4)}{((91 + 60) \times 5)} := \frac{((7 - (3 - (2 + 8))) \times 4)}{((9 - (1 - (6 - 0))) \times 5)}$

$$:= \frac{((7 - (3 \times (2 - 8))) \times 4)}{((9 + (16 - 0)) \times 5)} := \frac{((7 - (3 - 2)) \times (8 + 4))}{(91 - (6 + (0 - 5)))} := \frac{((7 - (3 - 28))^4)}{(((9 - 1)^6 + 0) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 \times ((3 - 2) \times 8)) - 4)}{((9 + (1 + (60 - 5))))} := \frac{((7 \times (3 \times (2 \times 8))) + 4)}{((91 - (6 - 0)) \times 5)} := \frac{((7 \times (32 + 8)) - 4)}{((9 + (1 \times 60)) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 \times 32) - (8 \times 4))}{((9 - 1) \times (6 \times (0 + 5)))} := \frac{((7 + ((3^2) - 8)) \times 4)}{((9 + (1 - (6 \times (0 - 5))))} := \frac{((7 + ((3 - 2) \times 8)) \times 4)}{(9 + (1 + (60 + 5)))}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 + (3 - (2 - 8))) \times 4)}{((9 + (1 + (6 - 0))) \times 5)} := \frac{((7 + (3 \times 2)) \times (8 \times 4))}{((9 - 1) \times (60 + 5))} := \frac{((7 + (32 - 8)) \times 4)}{((91 - 60) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 + 3) \times (2 \times (8 + 4)))}{((9 + 1) \times (6 \times (0 + 5)))} := \frac{((7 + 32) \times (8 + 4))}{((9 + 1) \times (60 + 5))} := \frac{((73 + 2) \times (8 \times 4))}{((9 + 1) \times (60 \times 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{((73 - 28) \times 4)}{(9 \times ((1 - 6) \times (0 - 5)))} := \frac{(7 - (3 - (2 \times (8 \times 4))))}{(91 - (6 - (0 \times 5)))} := \frac{(7 - (3 - (2 \times (8 + 4))))}{((9 - 16) \times (0 - 5))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (3 - (2^{8-4})))}{(9 + (16 - (0 \times 5)))} := \frac{(7 - (3 - (28 + 4)))}{(9 \times ((1^6 + 0) \times 5))} := \frac{(7 \times (((3^2) + 8) \times 4))}{(((9 + 1) \times 60) - 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 \times ((3 - (2 - 8)) \times 4))}{(9 \times ((1 + (6 - 0)) \times 5))} := \frac{(7 + ((3^2) + (8 \times 4)))}{((9 + 1) \times (6 - (0 \times 5)))} := \frac{(7 + (3 - (2 - (8 \times 4))))}{((9 + (1^6 + 0)) \times 5)}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (3 - (2 - (8 - 4))))}{(9 + (1 \times (6 - (0 \times 5))))} := \frac{(7 + (3 - (2 + (8 - 4))))}{(9 + ((1^6 + 0) - 5))} := \frac{(7 + (3 + (2 - (8 - 4))))}{(9 + (1^{605}))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (3 + (2 + (8 \times 4))))}{(((9 + 1) \times (6 - 0)) - 5)} := \frac{(7 + (3 + (2 + (8 + 4))))}{(9 + (16 - (0 - 5)))} := \frac{(7 + (3 + (2 + (8 - 4))))}{(9 + (1 \times (6 - (0 - 5))))}$$

$$:= \frac{7328 + 4}{9160 + 5} \quad := \frac{7328 - 4}{9160 - 5}$$

► $\frac{75368}{94210} := \frac{(((7 \times 5) - (3 \times 6)) \times 8)}{((9 + (4 \times 2)) \times 10)} := \frac{(((7^5-3) - 6) \times 8)}{(9 + (421 - 0))} := \frac{(((7 + (5 - 3))^6) \times 8)}{((9^4+2) \times 10)}$

$$:= \frac{(((7 + 5) \times (3 \times 6)) - 8)}{((9 + 4) \times (2 \times 10))} := \frac{(((7 + 5) \times (3 + 6)) + 8)}{((9 \times (4^2)) + (1 - 0))} := \frac{(((7 + 5) \times (3 + 6)) - 8)}{((9 - 4)^{2+1+0})}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 - (5 - (3 + 6))) \times 8)}{((9 + (4 - 2)) \times 10)} := \frac{((7 - (5 - 36)) \times 8)}{(((9 \times 4) + 2) \times 10)} := \frac{((7 \times ((5 - 3) \times 6)) - 8)}{(94 + (2 - (1 - 0)))}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 \times (5 - (3 - 6))) + 8)}{((9^4-2) - (1 - 0))} := \frac{((7 \times (5 - (3 - 6))) - 8)}{((9 - 4) \times (2 + 10))} := \frac{((7 \times (5 - 3)) - (6 - 8))}{(((9 - 4) \times 2) + 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 + (5 - (3 + 6))) \times 8)}{((9 - (4 + 2)) \times 10)} := \frac{((7 + (5 - (3 - 6))) \times 8)}{((9 + (4 + 2)) \times 10)} := \frac{((7 + (53 - 6)) \times 8)}{(9 \times ((4 + 2) \times 10))}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 + 53) \times (6 + 8))}{((9 - 4) \times 210)} := \frac{((7 - 5) \times ((3 + 6) \times 8))}{(9 \times ((4 - 2) \times 10))} := \frac{((7 - 5) \times (3 \times 68))}{((9 + 42) \times 10)}$$

$$:= \frac{((7 - 5) \times 368)}{((94 - 2) \times 10)} := \frac{((75 + (3 - 6)) \times 8)}{(9 \times (4 \times (2 \times 10)))} := \frac{(7 - (5 - (3 \times (6 + 8))))}{((9 \times (4 + 2)) + (1 - 0))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 - (5 + (3 \times (6 - 8))))}{(9 + (4 - (2 + (1 - 0))))} := \frac{(7 \times (5 - (3 + (6 - 8))))}{(9 + ((4^2) + 10))} := \frac{(7 + ((5 \times 3) + (6 - 8)))}{(9 + (4 + (2 + 10)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + ((5^3) + (6 \times 8)))}{(9 \times (4 + (21 - 0)))} := \frac{(7 + ((5^3) + 68))}{((9 + (4^2)) \times 10)} := \frac{(7 + (5 - ((3 - 6) \times 8)))}{(9 \times (4 + (2 - (1 - 0))))}$$

$$:= \frac{(7 + (5 \times (3 + (6 + 8))))}{(94 + (21 - 0))} := \frac{(7 + (5^{3+6-8}))}{(9 + (4 + (2 \times (1 - 0))))} := \frac{(7 + (5 + ((3 + 6) \times 8)))}{((9 - 4) \times (21 - 0))}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(7 + (5 + (36 + 8)))}{((9 - (4 - 2)) \times 10)} &:= \frac{(7 + (5 + (36 - 8)))}{(9 + (42 - (1 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(7 + (53 + (6 \times 8)))}{(9 \times ((4^2) - (1 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(75 - (3 + 68))}{(9 + (4 + (2 - 10)))} &:= \frac{(75 + (3 - (6 - 8)))}{((9 - 4) \times (2 \times 10))} &
 \end{aligned}$$

3.35 36 Equivalent Blocks

► $\frac{15642}{70389}$:= $\frac{(((1 + 5) \times 6) + 4) \times 2}{((7^{03}) + (8 + 9))}$:= $\frac{(((15 \times 6) + 4) \times 2)}{((70 + (3 \times 8)) \times 9)}$:= $\frac{((1 - (5 - (6 + 4)))^2)}{((7 - (0 - (3 + 8))) \times 9)}$

:= $\frac{((1 + ((5 + 6) \times 4)) \times 2)}{((7 - (0 - 38)) \times 9)}$:= $\frac{((1 + (5 \times (6 - 4))) \times 2)}{(7 - (0 - (3 + 89)))}$:= $\frac{((1 + (5 + (6 - 4)))^2)}{((7 + (0 - 3)) \times (8 \times 9))}$

:= $\frac{((1 + 5) \times ((6 \times 4) + 2))}{(703 + (8 - 9))}$:= $\frac{((1 + 5) \times (6^{4-2}))}{((70 + 38) \times 9)}$:= $\frac{(1 - (5 - ((6 + 4)^2)))}{((7^{03}) + 89)}$

:= $\frac{(1 - (5 - (6 \times (4^2))))}{((70 - (3 \times 8)) \times 9)}$:= $\frac{(1 - (5 - (6 \times (4 - 2))))}{(7 - (0 - (38 - 9)))}$:= $\frac{(1 - (5 - (6 + (4 - 2))))}{((7 - (0 - (3 - 8))) \times 9)}$

:= $\frac{(1 - (5 - (64 + 2)))}{((7 - (0 - (3 \times 8))) \times 9)}$:= $\frac{(1 - (5 - (64 - 2)))}{(1 - (5 - (64 - 2)))}$:= $\frac{(1 - (5 + (6 - (4^2))))}{(7 - (0 - (3 + (8 + 9))))}$

:= $\frac{(1 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 4)) - 2))}{((70 - (3 + 8)) \times 9)}$:= $\frac{(1 \times ((5 \times (6 - 4)) + 2))}{(7 - (0 - (38 + 9)))}$:= $\frac{(1 \times ((5 + (6 + 4)) \times 2))}{((7 - ((0 \times 3) - 8)) \times 9)}$

:= $\frac{(1 \times ((5 + 6) \times (4 \times 2)))}{(7 - (0 - 389))}$:= $\frac{(1 \times ((5 + 6) \times (4^2)))}{(703 + 89)}$:= $\frac{(1 \times (5 \times ((6 \times 4) + 2)))}{((70 + (3 - 8)) \times 9)}$

:= $\frac{(1 \times (5 \times (6 - (4 - 2))))}{(70 + (3 + (8 + 9)))}$:= $\frac{(1 \times (5 \times (6 + (4 \times 2))))}{(7 \times (0 - ((3 - 8) \times 9)))}$:= $\frac{(1 \times (56 \times (4 + 2)))}{(7 \times (0 + (3 \times (8 \times 9))))}$

:= $\frac{(1 \times (56 \times (4 - 2)))}{(7 \times ((0 \times 3) + (8 \times 9)))}$:= $\frac{(1 + ((5^{6-4}) - 2))}{((7 + (0 - (3 - 8))) \times 9)}$:= $\frac{(1 + (5 - (6 - (4^2))))}{((7 \times (0 \times 3)) + (8 \times 9))}$

:= $\frac{(1 + (5 - (6 - (4 - 2))))}{(7 - (0 - (3 + (8 - 9))))}$:= $\frac{(1 + (5 + ((6 + 4) \times 2)))}{(((7 \times (0 + 3)) - 8) \times 9)}$:= $\frac{(1 + (5 + (6 \times (4^2))))}{(70 + 389)}$

:= $\frac{(1 + (5 + (6 + (4 - 2))))}{(7 \times ((0 \times 38) + 9))}$:= $\frac{(156 - (4 + 2))}{((70 - (3 - 8)) \times 9)}$:= $\frac{(156 - (4 - 2))}{(7 \times (0 + ((3 + 8) \times 9)))}$

:= $\frac{(156 + (4 + 2))}{((70 + (3 + 8)) \times 9)}$:= $\frac{1564 + 2}{7038 + 9}$:= $\frac{1564 - 2}{7038 - 9}$

► $\frac{21054}{73689}$:= $\frac{(((2 \times 10) + 5) \times 4)}{((7^3) + (6 - (8 - 9)))}$:= $\frac{((2 - (1 \times (0 - 5))) \times 4)}{(7 \times (3 - (6 - (8 + 9))))}$:= $\frac{((2 - (1 + (0 - 5))) \times 4)}{(73 - (6 - (8 + 9)))}$

:= $\frac{((2 - (1 + (0 - 5)))^4)}{(7 \times ((3 + 6) \times (8 \times 9)))}$:= $\frac{((2 \times (1 - (0 - 5))) + 4)}{(7 \times (3 + (6 + (8 - 9))))}$:= $\frac{((2 \times (1 - (0 - 5))) - 4)}{(7 + (3 \times (6 - (8 - 9))))}$

:= $\frac{((2 \times (1 \times (0 + 5))) + 4)}{(7 + (3 + ((6 \times 8) - 9)))}$:= $\frac{((2 \times (10 \times 5)) - 4)}{((7^3) - (6 - (8 - 9)))}$:= $\frac{((2 \times (10 + 5)) + 4)}{(((7 + (3 + 6)) \times 8) - 9)}$

:= $\frac{((2 \times 10) + 54)}{(7 \times (36 - (8 - 9)))}$:= $\frac{((2 \times 105) + 4)}{(7 \times ((3 \times 6) + 89))}$:= $\frac{((2 \times (1 - (0 - 5))) + 4)}{(7 + (3 \times (68 + 9)))}$

:= $\frac{((2 + (1 - (0 - 5))) \times 4)}{(7 + (3 + (6 \times (8 + 9))))}$:= $\frac{((2 + (1 - 0)) \times 54)}{(7 \times (3 + (6 + (8 \times 9))))}$:= $\frac{(2 - (1 \times (0 - (5 \times 4))))}{(((7 + 3) \times 6) + (8 + 9))}$

:= $\frac{(2 \times ((1 - (0 - 5)) \times 4))}{(73 + (6 + 89))}$:= $\frac{(2 \times ((1 - (0 - 5))^4))}{(7 \times (3 \times (6 \times (8 \times 9))))}$:= $\frac{(2 \times ((10 + 5) \times 4))}{(7 \times (3 + ((6 \times 8) + 9)))}$

:= $\frac{(2 \times (1 - (0 - (5 \times 4))))}{(7 \times (3 \times (6 - (8 - 9))))}$:= $\frac{(2 \times (1 - (0 - (5 + 4))))}{(7 \times (3 + (6 - (8 - 9))))}$:= $\frac{(2 \times (1 - (0 - 54)))}{(7 + (3 \times ((6 + 8) \times 9)))}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (1 \times (0 + (5 + 4))))}{(7 \times (3 - (6 \times (8 - 9))))} := \frac{(2 \times (10 \times (5 + 4)))}{(7 \times ((3 \times 6) + (8 \times 9)))} := \frac{(2 \times (10^{5+4}))}{(7 \times (((3 \times 6) - 8)^9))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (10 + (5 + 4)))}{(7 \times (36 - (8 + 9)))} := \frac{(2 \times (1 - (0 - (5 - 4))))}{(73 - (68 - 9))} := \frac{(2 \times (1 - (0 \times 54)))}{7^{(3+6-8)^9}} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + ((1 - (0 - 5)) \times 4))}{(73 - ((6 - 8) \times 9))} := \frac{(2 + ((1^{05}) \times 4))}{(7 + (3 - (6 - (8 + 9))))} := \frac{(2 + ((10 + 5) \times 4))}{((7^3) - ((6 + 8) \times 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (1 - (0 - (5 + 4))))}{(7 + (36 + (8 - 9)))} := \frac{(2 + (10 + 54))}{(7 \times ((3 \times (6 + 8)) - 9))} := \frac{(2 + 1054)}{(7 + 3689)} \\
 &:= \frac{(21 - (0 - (5 + 4)))}{(7 + (3 + (6 + 89)))} := \frac{(21 \times ((0 \times 5) + 4))}{(7 \times (3 + ((6 \times 8) - 9)))} := \frac{(210 \times (5 - 4))}{(7 \times (3 + (6 \times (8 + 9))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{47368}{59210}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((4 \times (7 \times 3)) + 6) \times 8)}{(5 \times (9 \times (2 \times 10)))} := \frac{(((4 \times (7 + 3)) + 6) \times 8)}{(5 \times (92 \times (1 - 0)))} := \frac{(((4 \times (7 - 3)) - 6) \times 8)}{((5 \times (9 \times 2)) + 10)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((4 + (7 - 3)) \times 6) - 8)}{(5 \times (9 + (2 - (1 - 0))))} := \frac{(((4 - (7 - (3 \times 6))) \times 8)}{(5 \times (9 + (21 - 0)))} := \frac{((4 \times ((7 \times 3) + 6)) + 8)}{(5 \times (9 + (2 \times 10)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times (7 + (3 \times 6))) + 8)}{(5 \times (9 \times (2 + (1 - 0))))} := \frac{((4 \times (73 + 6)) + 8)}{(5 \times (9^{2 \times 1 + 0}))} := \frac{((4 \times 73) + 68)}{((5 \times 92) - 10)} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times 73) - 68)}{((5 + 9) \times (2 \times 10))} := \frac{((4 + (7 - (3 - 6))) \times 8)}{(5 \times ((9 \times 2) + 10))} := \frac{((4 + (7 + (3 - 6))) \times 8)}{((5 \times (9 \times 2)) - 10)} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 + (7 + 36)) \times 8)}{((5 \times 92) + 10)} := \frac{(4 - ((7 - (3 \times 6)) \times 8))}{(5 + ((9 + 2) \times 10))} := \frac{(4 - ((7 - (3 + 6)) \times 8))}{((5 \times (9 - 2)) - 10)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (7 - (3 + 68)))}{(5 \times (9 - (2 - 10)))} := \frac{(4 \times ((7 - (3 - 6)) \times 8))}{(4 \times ((7 - (3 - 6)) \times 8))} := \frac{(4 \times ((7 \times (3 + 6)) + 8))}{(4 \times ((7 - (3 - 6)) \times 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times ((7 + (3 - 6)) \times 8))}{((5 + (9 + 2)) \times 10)} := \frac{(4 \times (7 - (3 - (6 + 8))))}{(5 \times ((9^2) - (1 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times (7 - (3 \times (6 - 8))))}{(5 \times ((9^2) - 10))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (7 - (3 + (6 - 8))))}{(5 \times (9 - (2 + (1 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 \times (7 \times ((3 \times 6) - 8))}{(4 \times (7 - (3 - (6 + 8))))} := \frac{(4 \times (7^3 + 6 - 8))}{(4 \times (7 - (3 \times (6 - 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (7 + ((3 + 6) \times 8))}{((5 \times (9^2)) - 10)} := \frac{(4 \times (7 + (3 - (6 - 8))))}{(5 \times (9 + (2 + (1 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 \times (7 + (3 + (6 + 8))))}{((5 + (9 - 2)) \times 10)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (7 + (3 + (6 - 8))))}{(5 \times (9 - (2 - (1 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 \times (7 + (36 + 8)))}{((5 \times 9) + 210)} := \frac{(4^{7+3 \times (6-8)})}{(5^{9+2-10})} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + ((7 - (3 - 6)) \times 8))}{(5 \times (9 + (2 + 10)))} := \frac{(4 + ((7 + (3 - 6)) \times 8))}{(5 \times (9 \times (2 - 1 + 0)))} := \frac{(4 + ((7 - 3) \times (6 + 8)))}{(5 + ((9 - 2) \times 10))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (7 - (3 - 68)))}{(5 \times ((9 \times 2) + (1 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 + (7 + (3 + (6 - 8))))}{(5 + (9 + (2 - (1 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 + 7368)}{(5 + 9210)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{9273}{185460}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((9^2) - 7) \times 3)}{(185 \times (4 \times (6 - 0)))} := \frac{((9 \times (2 \times 7)) - 3)}{(((1 + 8) \times 5) - 4) \times 60} := \frac{((9 \times 2) - (7 - 3))}{(1 \times ((85 \times 4) - 60))} \\
 &:= \frac{((9 \times 27) + 3)}{((1 + (85 - 4)) \times 60)} := \frac{((9^{2+7}) \times 3)}{(((1 + 8)^{5+4}) \times 60)} := \frac{((9^2) - (7 \times 3))}{((1^8) \times (5 \times (4 \times 60)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((9 + (2 \times 7)) \times 3)}{(1 \times ((8 - 5) \times 460))} := \frac{((9 + (2 - 7)) \times 3)}{((1^{85}) \times (4 \times 60))} := \frac{((9 - 2) \times (7 \times 3))}{(((1 + 8) \times 5) + 4) \times 60} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 - ((2 - 7) \times 3))}{(1 \times (8 \times (54 + (6 - 0))))} := \frac{(9 - (2 - (7 - 3)))}{(1 \times ((8 \times (5 \times 4)) + 60))} := \frac{(9 - (2 \times (7 - 3)))}{((1^8) - (5 - (4 \times (6 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 - (2 + (7 - 3)))}{(1 + (8 - (5 + (4 - 60))))} := \frac{(9 \times ((2 + 7) \times 3))}{(1 \times ((85 - 4) \times 60))} := \frac{(9 \times (2 \times (7 - 3)))}{(18 \times ((5 \times 4) + 60))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 \times (2^{7-3}))}{((1 + 8) \times (5 \times (4 + 60)))} := \frac{(9 \times (2 + (7 \times 3)))}{(18 \times (5 \times (46 - 0)))} := \frac{(9 \times (2 + (7 + 3)))}{(1 \times (((8 \times 5) - 4) \times 60))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 := \frac{(9 \times (2 + (7 - 3)))}{((1 + (8 + (5 + 4))) \times 60)} & := \frac{(9 \times (27 + 3))}{((1 + (85 + 4)) \times 60)} & := \frac{(9 \times (27 - 3))}{(1 \times (8 \times ((5 + 4) \times 60)))} \\
 := \frac{(9 \times 273)}{(1 + 8) \times 5460} & := \frac{(9 + ((2 \times 7) - 3))}{(1 \times (8 \times (5 \times (4 + (6 - 0)))))} & := \frac{(9 + ((2 + 7) \times 3))}{(1 \times ((8 - 5) \times (4 \times 60)))} \\
 := \frac{(9 + (2 - (7 - 3)))}{((1 + (8 + 5)) \times (4 + (6 - 0)))} & := \frac{(9 + (2 \times (7 \times 3)))}{(1 \times ((8 + (5 + 4)) \times 60))} & := \frac{(9 + (2^{7-3}))}{(1 \times ((8 \times 5) + 460))} \\
 := \frac{(9 + (2 + (7 \times 3)))}{(1 + (8 + ((5^4) + (6 - 0))))} & := \frac{(9 + (2 + (7 + 3)))}{(1 \times ((8 - (5 - 4)) \times 60))} & := \frac{(9 + (2 + (7 - 3)))}{(((1^{85}) + 4) \times 60)} \\
 := \frac{(9 + (2 + 73))}{(1 \times ((8 + (5 \times 4)) \times 60))} & := \frac{(9 + (27 + 3))}{((1 - (8 - (5 \times 4))) \times 60)} & := \frac{(9 + 273)}{(((18 \times 5) + 4) \times 60)} \\
 := \frac{(92 \times (7 + 3))}{(1 \times (8 \times (5 \times 460)))} & := \frac{(92 + (7 + 3))}{(1 \times (85 \times (4 \times (6 - 0))))} & := \frac{(92 + 73)}{(((1^8) + 54) \times 60)}
 \end{array}$$

3.36 37 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13902}{48657} := \frac{(((1 + 3)^9 + 0) \times 2)}{((4^{8+6-5}) \times 7)} & := \frac{((1 - (3 \times 9)) \times (0 - 2))}{((4 - (8 - (6 \times 5))) \times 7)} & := \frac{((1^3) \times (9 \times (0 + 2)))}{(4 + (8 - (6 - 57)))} \\
 := \frac{((1^3) \times (90 \times 2))}{((4 + (8 + 6)) \times (5 \times 7))} & := \frac{((1^3) \times (90 - 2))}{(4 \times ((8 + 6) \times 5) + 7)} & := \frac{((1^3) + (9^{02}))}{((4 \times 86) - 57)} \\
 := \frac{((1 + (3 \times (9 - 0))) \times 2)}{(4 \times (8 + (6 + (5 \times 7))))} & := \frac{((1 + (3 + (9 - 0))) \times 2)}{((4 + (8 + (6 - 5))) \times 7)} & := \frac{((1 + (39 - 0)) \times 2)}{(4 \times ((8 - 6) \times (5 \times 7)))} \\
 := \frac{((1 + 3) \times (9 \times (0 + 2)))}{(4 \times ((8 + (6 - 5)) \times 7))} & := \frac{((1 + 3) \times (90 \times 2))}{((4 + 8) \times (6 \times (5 \times 7)))} & := \frac{((13 - (9 - 0)) \times 2)}{(4 \times (8 - ((6 - 5)^7)))} \\
 := \frac{((1 - 3) \times (9 \times (0 - 2)))}{((48 - (6 \times 5)) \times 7)} & := \frac{(1 - (3 - (90 - 2)))}{(((4 \times 8) + (6 + 5)) \times 7)} & := \frac{(1 - (3 + (9 \times (0 - 2))))}{(4 \times (8 - (6 - (5 + 7))))} \\
 := \frac{(1 - (3 - 902))}{((4 + 86) \times (5 \times 7))} & := \frac{(1 \times ((3 + (9 - 0)) \times 2))}{(4 + (8 + (6 \times (5 + 7))))} & := \frac{(1 \times ((3 + (9 - 0))^2))}{((48 - 6) \times (5 + 7))} \\
 := \frac{(1 \times (3 \times (90 \times 2)))}{((48 + 6) \times (5 \times 7))} & := \frac{(1 \times (3 \times (90 - 2)))}{((4 + 8) \times ((6 + 5) \times 7))} & := \frac{(1 \times (3 + (9 - (0 \times 2))))}{(48 + (6 - (5 + 7)))} \\
 := \frac{(1 \times (3 + (9 - (0 - 2))))}{((4 - (8 - (6 + 5))) \times 7)} & := \frac{(1 \times (3 + (9^{02})))}{((4 + (8 + (6 \times 5))) \times 7)} & := \frac{(1 \times (3 + (9 + (0 - 2))))}{((4 \times (8 - (6 - 5))) + 7)} \\
 := \frac{(1 \times (39 \times (0 + 2)))}{((4 \times ((8 + 6) \times 5)) - 7)} & := \frac{(1 + (3 - (9 \times (0 \times 2))))}{(4 - (8 - (6 + (5 + 7))))} & := \frac{(1 + (3 \times (9 - (0 \times 2))))}{((4 + ((8 - 6) \times 5)) \times 7)} \\
 := \frac{((4 + (8 - (6 - 5))) \times 7)}{(1 + (3 \times (9 + (0 - 2))))} & := \frac{((4 + (8 \times (6 + 5))) \times 7)}{(1 + (3 + (90 \times 2)))} & := \frac{(4 \times (86 + (5 - 7)))}{(1 + (3 + (90 + 2)))} \\
 := \frac{(1 + (39 - (0 - 2)))}{(4 + (86 + 57))} & := \frac{(13 - (9 - (0 - 2)))}{((4 + (8 - (6 + 5))) \times 7)} & := \frac{(13 - (9 + (0 - 2)))}{((4 \times (8 - (6 - 5))) - 7)} \\
 := \frac{(13 + (9^{02}))}{((4 + ((8 \times 6) - 5)) \times 7)} & := \frac{(13 + (9 + (0 - 2)))}{(4 + (8 + (65 - 7)))} & := \frac{1390 + 2}{4865 + 7} \\
 := \frac{1390 - 2}{4865 - 7} & &
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14076}{98532} := \frac{(((1 + (4 - 0)) \times 7) - 6)}{(((9 \times 8) - 5) \times 3) + 2} & := \frac{((1^{4+0 \times 7}) + 6)}{(9 + (8 \times (5 \times (3 - 2))))} & := \frac{((1^4 + 0) \times (7 + 6))}{(((9 + 8) \times 5) + (3 \times 2))} \\
 := \frac{((1^4 + 0) \times 76)}{(9 - 8) \times 532} & := \frac{((1^4 + 0) + (7 + 6))}{(98 - (5 - (3 + 2)))} & := \frac{((1^4 + 0) + (7 - 6))}{(9 - (8 - ((5 \times 3) - 2)))}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(1+40) \times (7 \times 6)}{(98 \times ((5^3) - 2))} &:= \frac{((14 \times (0+7)) + 6)}{((9^{8-5}) - (3-2))} &:= \frac{(1 - ((4 \times (0-7)) + 6))}{(9 - (8 - (5 \times 32)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - ((4 \times (0-7)) - 6))}{((9 \times ((8-5)^3)) + 2)} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((4 - (0-7)) \times 6))}{(((9 \times 8) + 5) \times (3 \times 2))} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((4 \times (0+7)) + 6))}{((9+8) \times (5 + (3^2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 - (0 - (7 \times 6))))}{((9 \times 8) + ((5^3) \times 2))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 - (0 \times 76)))}{(9 - (8 + (5 - 32)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 + (0 - (7 - 6))))}{(9 + (8 - (5 - (3^2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (40 - (7 + 6)))}{(9 \times (8 + ((5 \times 3) - 2)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (40 \times (7 - 6)))}{(((9+85) \times 3) - 2)} &:= \frac{(1 \times (40 + (7 \times 6)))}{((9 \times (8^{5-3})) - 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{1^4 + 0 \times 76}{(9 - (8 - (5 + (3 - 2))))} &:= \frac{(1 + ((40 \times 7) + 6))}{(9 + (8 \times ((5^3) \times 2)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (4 - ((0 \times 7) - 6)))}{((9 \times 8) + (5 \times (3 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (4 - (0 - (7 + 6))))}{(9 \times (8 + (5 + (3 - 2))))} &:= \frac{(1 + (4 - (0 - (7 - 6))))}{(9 + (8 + (5 \times (3 + 2))))} &:= \frac{(1 + (4 - (0 \times 76)))}{((9 \times 8) - (5 + 32))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (4 - (0 - 76)))}{(9 \times (8 + (53 + 2)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (40 \times (7 - 6)))}{(((9+8)^{5-3}) - 2)} &:= \frac{(1 + (40 + (7 - 6)))}{((9 + (8 \times 5)) \times (3 \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 \times (85 + (3 \times 2)))}{(1 + (40 + 76))} &:= \frac{(14 - ((0 \times 7) - 6))}{((9 + (8 + 53)) \times 2)} &:= \frac{(14 - (0 - (7 \times 6)))}{((9 \times (8 \times 5)) + 32)} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 \times (85 + (3 \times 2)))}{(14 - (0 - (7 - 6)))} &:= \frac{(9 + (8 + 53)) \times 2}{(14 - (0 - 76))} &:= \frac{(9 \times (8 \times 5)) + 32}{(14 \times ((0 \times 7) + 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 + ((8 - 5) \times 32))}{(14 \times (0 + (7 + 6)))} &:= \frac{(98 + 532)}{(14 + ((0 \times 7) - 6))} &:= \frac{(98 \times (5 + (3 - 2)))}{(140 \times (7 - 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(98 \times ((5 \times 3) - 2))}{(140 + 76)} &:= \frac{(9 - (8 - (53 + 2)))}{(9 - (8 - (53 + 2)))} &:= \frac{(98 \times (5 + (3 + 2)))}{(98 \times (5 + (3 + 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(140 + 76)}{(9 \times (8 + (5 \times 32)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{3297}{164850}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((3^2) \times 9) + 7)}{((1 + (6 + 4)) \times (8 \times 50))} &:= \frac{(((3 + 2) \times 9) - 7)}{(1 \times ((6 + (4 \times 8)) \times 50))} &:= \frac{(((3 - 2)^9) + 7)}{((16^4) \times (8 \times 50))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 - (2 - 9))^7)}{(1 \times (((6 + 4)^8) \times (5 - 0)))} &:= \frac{((3 \times (2 + 9)) + 7)}{(((16^6) + 4) \times (8 \times 50))} &:= \frac{((3 \times (2 + 9)) - 7)}{(1 + ((6^4) + (8 - (5 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times 2) - (9 - 7))}{((16 - (4 + 8)) \times 50)} &:= \frac{((3 \times 2)^{9-7})}{(((1 + 6) \times 4) + 8) \times 50} &:= \frac{((3 \times 29) - 7)}{(1 \times ((6 + 4) \times (8 \times 50)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3^2) \times (9 - 7))}{(1 \times ((6 + (4 + 8)) \times 50))} &:= \frac{((3^2) + (9 \times 7))}{(1 \times (6 \times ((4 + 8) \times 50)))} &:= \frac{((3^2) + (9 - 7))}{((1 + (6 - (4 - 8))) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 + 2) \times (9 - 7))}{(1 \times ((6 - (4 - 8)) \times 50))} &:= \frac{((3 + 29) \times 7)}{((1 + 6) \times (4 \times (8 \times 50)))} &:= \frac{((3 - 2) \times (9 - 7))}{(1 \times ((6 + (4 - 8)) \times 50))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 - 2) \times 97)}{((16^6) \times 4850)} &:= \frac{((3 - 2)^{9-7})}{(1 \times (6 + (4 + (8 \times (5 - 0))))))} &:= \frac{(3 - ((2 - 9) \times 7))}{((1 + 64) \times (8 \times (5 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (2 - (9 \times 7)))}{((16 + 48) \times 50)} &:= \frac{(3 - (2 - (9 + 7)))}{((1 + ((6 - 4) \times 8)) \times 50)} &:= \frac{(3 - (2 - (9 - 7)))}{((1 + (6 + (4 - 8))) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times ((2 \times 9) - 7))}{((1 + ((6 \times 4) + 8)) \times 50)} &:= \frac{(3 \times (2 \times (9 + 7)))}{((16 - 4) \times (8 \times 50))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (2 \times 97))}{(1 \times (6 \times 4850))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (2^{9-7}))}{((16 + (4 - 8)) \times 50)} &:= \frac{(3 \times (2 + (9 + 7)))}{(1 \times ((6 + 48) \times 50))} &:= \frac{3^{2^{9-7}}}{((1 + ((6 + 4) \times 8)) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + ((2 \times 9) + 7))}{((16 + (4 + 8)) \times 50)} &:= \frac{(3 + (2^{9-7}))}{((1 - (6 - (4 + 8))) \times 50)} &:= \frac{(3 + (2 + (9 \times 7)))}{((16^6) \times (4 \times 850))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (29 + 7))}{((1 + (6 + (4 \times 8))) \times 50)} &:= \frac{(3 + (29 - 7))}{((1 - (6 \times (4 - 8))) \times 50)} &:= \frac{(32 - (9 + 7))}{(1 \times ((6 - 4) \times (8 \times 50)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(32 \times (9 + 7))}{(1 \times (64 \times (8 \times 50)))} &:= \frac{(32 + (9 + 7))}{((16 + (4 \times 8)) \times 50)} &:= \frac{(32 + (9 - 7))}{(1 \times ((6 - 4) \times 850))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(329 + 7)}{((1 + 6) \times (48 \times 50))}$$

3.37 38 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{14658}{73290} &:= \frac{(((1^4) + 6) \times (5^8))}{(7 \times ((3 + 2)^9 + 0))} := \frac{(((1 + (4 \times 6)) \times 5) + 8)}{(7 \times (3 + (2 + 90)))} := \frac{(((1 + (4 + 6)) \times 5) + 8)}{(7 \times ((3 + 2) \times (9 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(((14 + 6) \times 5) + 8)}{((7 - (3 - 2)) \times 90)} := \frac{(((1 - (4 - (6 \times 5))) \times 8)}{((7 + (3 + 2)) \times 90)} := \frac{(((1^4) + (6 - (5 - 8)))}{((7 \times 3) + (29 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + (4 \times (6 + 5))) \times 8)}{((7 + 3) \times (2 \times 90))} := \frac{((1 - 46) \times (5 - 8))}{((73 + 2) \times (9 - 0))} := \frac{(1 - ((4 - 6) \times 58))}{(73 + (2^9 + 0))} \\ &:= \frac{((1 - (4 - (6 - (5 - 8))))}{(1 - (4 - (6 + (5 \times 8))))} := \frac{(1 - (4 - (6 + (5 \times 8))))}{(1 - (4 - (6 + (5 \times 8))))} := \frac{(1 - (4 - (6 + (5 \times 8))))}{(1 - (4 - (6 + (5 \times 8))))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + (32 - (9 - 0)))}{(1 - (4 - (65 + 8)))} := \frac{((7 \times 32) - (9 - 0))}{(1 - (4 + (6 - (5 \times 8))))} := \frac{(73 - (2 - (9 - 0)))}{(1 - (46 \times (5 - 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{((7^3) - (2 - (9 - 0)))}{(1 \times (((4 \times 6) + 5) \times 8))} := \frac{((73 \times 2) + (9 - 0))}{(1 \times (((4 + 6) \times 5) + 8))} := \frac{(((7^3) \times 2) + (9 - 0))}{(1 \times ((4 \times 6) + (5 - 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{((7 - 3) \times 290)}{(1 \times ((4 + 6) \times 58))} := \frac{((7 + 3) \times (29 - 0))}{(1 \times (4 - ((6 - 5)^8))} := \frac{(7 \times ((3 \times 2) + (9 - 0)))}{(1 \times (4 - (6 - (5 \times 8))))} \\ &:= \frac{((7 + 3) \times 290)}{(1 \times (4 - (6 - (5 + 8))))} := \frac{(7 - (3 - (2 + (9 - 0))))}{(1 \times (4 - (6 \times (5 - 8))))} := \frac{(7 + (3 + (2 \times 90)))}{(1 \times (4 \times (6 - (5 - 8))))} \\ &:= \frac{(73 - (2 \times (9 - 0)))}{(1 \times (4 \times (6 + (5 \times 8))))} := \frac{((7 + 3) \times (2 + (9 - 0)))}{(1 \times (4 + (6 - (5 - 8))))} := \frac{((7 - (3 + 2)) \times 90)}{(1 \times (46 + (5 + 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{((7 + 3) \times (2 + 90))}{(1 + ((4 - (6 - 5)) \times 8))} := \frac{(7 - (32 - 90))}{(1 + (4 - (6 + (5 - 8))))} := \frac{(7 + (32 \times (9 - 0)))}{(1 + (4 \times ((6 - 5) \times 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{((7 \times (3 + 2)) + 90)}{(1 + (4^{(6-5)^8}))} := \frac{(1 + (4^{6+5-8}))}{((7^3) - (2 \times (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + (4 + (6 - (5 - 8))))}{(7 \times (3 - (2 - (9 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (4 + (6 + (5 \times 8))))}{((7^3) + (2 - 90))} := \frac{(1 + (4 + (6 + (5 - 8))))}{(7 + (3 \times (2 + (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 + (46 + (5 \times 8)))}{((7^3) + (2 + 90))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (46 + (5 + 8)))}{(7 + (3 + 290))} := \frac{(14 \times (6 - (5 - 8)))}{(7 \times ((3 - 2) \times 90))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{18546}{92730} &:= \frac{(((1 + 8) \times 5) + 4) \times 6}{(9 - 2) \times (7 \times 30)} := \frac{(((1 + 8) \times (5 \times 4)) + 6)}{(927 + (3 - 0))} := \frac{(((1 + 8)^{5+4}) \times 6)}{((9^{2+7}) \times 30)} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + (8 \times (5 - 4))) \times 6)}{(9 \times (27 + (3 - 0)))} := \frac{((1 + (8 + (5 + 4))) \times 6)}{((9 + (2 + 7)) \times 30)} := \frac{((1 + (8 - 5)) \times 46)}{(92 \times (7 + (3 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + 8) \times (5 + (4 + 6)))}{(9 \times (2 + (73 - 0)))} := \frac{((1 + 8) \times 546)}{(9 \times 2730)} := \frac{((1 - 8) \times (5 \times (4 - 6)))}{(9 - (2 - (7^3 + 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{((18 + (5 + 4)) \times 6)}{((9^2) \times (7 + (3 - 0)))} := \frac{((18 + (5 - 4)) \times 6)}{(((9^2) \times 7) + (3 - 0))} := \frac{(1 - (8 - (5 + (4 \times 6))))}{((9 + 2) \times (7 + (3 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (8 + (5 \times (4 - 6))))}{(9 + (2 + (7 - (3 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 \times (((8 \times 5) - 4) \times 6))}{((9 + 27) \times 30)} := \frac{(1 \times ((8 \times (5 + 4)) - 6))}{(((9 \times 2) - 7) \times 30)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times ((8 - 5) \times 46))}{((9 + (2 \times 7)) \times 30)} := \frac{(1 \times ((85 - 4) \times 6))}{(9 \times ((2 + 7) \times 30))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 - (5 \times (4 - 6))))}{(9 + (27 \times (3 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 - (5 + (4 - 6))))}{(9 + (2^{7-3+0}))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 \times ((5 - 4) \times 6)))}{((9 \times 27) - (3 - 0))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (5 + (4 - 6))))}{((9 + (2 - 7)) \times 30)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(1 \times (8 + (5 - (4 - 6))))}{(((9 \times 2) + 7) \times (3 - 0))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 + (5 + (4 + 6))))}{(92 - (7 - 30))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 + (5 + (4 - 6))))}{(9 - (2 \times (7 - 30)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (85 - (4 - 6)))}{(92 + (7^3 + 0))} := \frac{(1 + ((8 \times 5) - (4 \times 6)))}{((9^2) + (7 - (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + ((8 \times 5) + (4 + 6)))}{((92 - 7) \times (3 - 0))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + ((8 - 5) \times (4 + 6)))}{(9 + (2 \times (73 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + ((8 - 5) \times 46))}{(9 + (2 \times (7^3 + 0)))} := \frac{(1 + (8 - (5 - (4 \times 6))))}{(9 + ((2^7) + (3 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (8 - (5 - (4 + 6))))}{((9 - 2) \times (7 + (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + (8 - (5 + (4 - 6))))}{(9 - (2 + (7 - 30)))} := \frac{(1 + (8 + (5 - (4 + 6))))}{(9 + ((2 \times 7) - (3 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (8 + (5 - (4 - 6))))}{(9 - (2 - (73 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + (8 + (5 + (4 - 6))))}{((9^2) - (7 \times (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + (85 + (4 - 6)))}{(9 - (2 - 7)) \times 30} \\
 & := \frac{(18 + (5 + (4 + 6)))}{(92 + (73 - 0))} := \frac{(185 + 46)}{((9 \times (2^7)) + (3 - 0))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{20534}{71869}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(((2^{05}) + 3) \times 4)}{(7 \times ((1^8) + 69))} := \frac{(((2^{05}) - 3) \times 4)}{(7 \times (1 + ((8 \times 6) + 9)))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + (5^3))) + 4)}{(7 \times (1 + ((8 + 6) \times 9)))} \\
 & := \frac{((2 \times (0 + (5 + 3))) + 4)}{(7 + (1 + (8 + (6 \times 9))))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + 53)) + 4)}{(7 \times ((1^8) + (6 \times 9)))} := \frac{((2^{053}) \times 4)}{(7 \times (1 \times ((8 - 6)^9)))} \\
 & := \frac{((2^{053}) - 4)}{(7 \times (1 \times ((8 + 6) \times 9)))} := \frac{((2^{05}) + 34)}{(7 \times (18 + (6 + 9)))} := \frac{((20 - (5 + 3)) \times 4)}{(7 \times (1 + (8 + (6 + 9))))} \\
 & := \frac{((20 \times (5 + 3)) - 4)}{(7 \times (1 + (8 + 69)))} := \frac{((20 - 5) \times (3 \times 4))}{(((7 + 1) \times 8) + 6) \times 9} := \frac{(2 - ((0 \times 5) - 34))}{(7 - (1 - (8 \times (6 + 9))))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 - (0 - ((5 - 3)^4)))}{(7 \times ((1^{86}) \times 9))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (5 - (3 - 4))))}{(7 + (18 - (6 - 9)))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (5 + (3 + 4))))}{(((7 + 1) \times 8) - (6 + 9))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 - (0 - (5 + (3 - 4))))}{(7 \times (18 - (6 + 9)))} := \frac{(2 - (0 \times (5 - 34)))}{7 \times 1^{869}} := \frac{(2 - (0 - 534))}{(7 + 1869)} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times (0 - (5 \times (3 - 4))))}{(7 \times (1 \times (8 + (6 - 9))))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + ((5 \times 3) + 4))}{(7 \times (1 + ((8 - 6) \times 9)))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + ((5 \times 3) - 4))}{(7 \times (1 \times (8 - (6 - 9))))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times (0 + ((5^3) - 4))}{(7 \times (1 + (8 \times (6 + 9))))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (5 - (3 - 4))))}{(7 \times (1 + (8 + (6 - 9))))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (5 + (3 + 4))))}{(7 + (1 \times (8 + 69)))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (5 + 34))}{(7 \times (1 \times ((8 \times 6) - 9)))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (53 + 4))}{(7 \times (1 \times ((8 \times 6) + 9)))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (53 - 4))}{(7 \times (18 - (6 + 9)))} \\
 & := \frac{(2^{-05+3 \times 4})}{(7 + ((1 + (8 \times 6)) \times 9))} := \frac{2^{-05+3+4}}{(7 - (1 \times (8 - (6 + 9))))} := \frac{(2^{-05 \times (3-4)})}{(7 \times ((1^8) + (6 + 9)))} \\
 & := \frac{(2^{05+3-4})}{(7 \times (1 - (8 - (6 + 9))))} := \frac{(20 \times ((5 - 3) \times 4))}{(7 + (1 + (8 \times 69)))} := \frac{(20 \times (5 + (3 + 4))}{(7 \times (1 \times (8 \times (6 + 9))))} \\
 & := \frac{(20 \times (5 + (3 - 4))}{(7 \times (1 + ((8 \times 6) - 9)))} := \frac{(20 + (5 \times 34))}{(7 \times (1 \times (86 + 9)))} := \frac{(205 - (3^4))}{(7 \times (1 - (8 - 69)))} \\
 & := \frac{(205 - (3 + 4))}{(7 \times ((18 \times 6) - 9))} := \frac{(205 - (3 - 4))}{(718 - (6 - 9))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{47328}{59160}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(((4 + 7) \times 3) + 2) \times 8}{(5 \times (9 + (1 + 60)))} := \frac{((4 - (7 - (3^2))) \times 8)}{(59 + (1^6 + 0))} := \frac{((4 \times (7 + (3 \times 2))) - 8)}{(5 - (9 + (1 - 60)))} \\
 & := \frac{((4 \times (7 + (3^2))) + 8)}{(5 + (91 - (6 - 0)))} := \frac{((4 \times (7 + 32)) + 8)}{((5 \times 9) + 160)} := \frac{((4 \times (73 \times 2)) - 8)}{(5 \times (9 \times (16 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{((4 \times (73 - 2)) - 8)}{(5 \times (9 + (1 \times 60)))} := \frac{((4^{7-3}) - (2 \times 8))}{(5 \times ((9 + 1) \times (6 - 0)))} := \frac{((4^{7-3}) + (2 \times 8))}{(5 \times (9 - (1 - 60)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{((4 + ((7 \times 3) + 2)) \times 8)}{(5 \times (9 \times (1 \times (6 - 0))))} := \frac{((4 + (7 \times (3 - 2))) \times 8)}{((5 \times (9 + 1)) + 60)} := \frac{((47 + 3) \times (2 + 8))}{(5^{9+1-6+0})} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times ((7 - (3 - 2)) \times 8))}{(5 \times ((9 - 1) \times (6 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times ((73 + 2) \times 8))}{(5 \times ((9 + 1) \times 60))} := \frac{(4 \times (7 - (3 - (2 + 8))))}{(5 \times (9 - (1 - (6 - 0))))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times (7 - (3 \times (2 - 8))))}{(5^{9-1 \times 6+0})} := \frac{(4 \times (7 - (3 + (2 - 8))))}{(5 \times (9 + (1^6 + 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times (7 \times ((3 + 2)^8))}{((5^9) \times (1 + (6 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times (7 \times (3 - (2 - 8))))}{(5 \times (9 \times (1 + (6 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 \times (7 \times (32 - 8)))}{((5 + (9 \times 1)) \times 60)} := \frac{(4 \times (7 + ((3 \times 2) + 8)))}{((5 \times (9 \times 1)) + 60)} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times (7 + ((3^2) + 8)))}{(59 + (1 + 60))} := \frac{(4 \times (7 + ((3^2) - 8)))}{(5 \times (9 - (1^6 + 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times (7 + ((3 - 2) \times 8)))}{(5 + (9 + (1 + 60)))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times (7 + (3 - (2 - 8))))}{(5 \times (9 + (1 + (6 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 \times (7 + (3 + (2 + 8))))}{((5 \times (9 - 1)) + 60)} := \frac{(4 \times (7 + (3 + (2 - 8))))}{(5 \times (9 + (1 - (6 - 0))))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times (7 + (32 - 8)))}{(5 \times (91 - 60))} := \frac{(4 + ((7 - (3 - 2)) \times 8))}{(5 + ((9 + 1) \times (6 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 + ((7 + 32) \times 8))}{((5 \times 91) - 60)} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + ((73 + 2) \times 8))}{(5 \times (91 + 60))} := \frac{(4 + (7 - (3 - 28)))}{(5 \times (9 \times (1^6 + 0)))} := \frac{(4 + (7 \times (3 \times (2 \times 8))))}{(5 \times (91 - (6 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + (7 + ((3^2) - 8))}{(5 + (9 + (1^6 + 0)))} := \frac{(4 + (7 + (3 - (2 - 8))))}{(5^{9-1-6+0})} := \frac{(4 + (7 + (3 + (2 + 8))))}{(5 + (9 + (16 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + (7 + (3 + (2 - 8))))}{(5 \times (9 - (1 + (6 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 + 7328)}{(5 + 9160)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► **67014**
89352

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{((6 \times (7 - 0)) - (1 - 4))}{(8 - ((9 - 35) \times 2))} := \frac{((6 \times (7 - 0)) + (1 - 4))}{((8 - (9 \times (3 - 5))) \times 2)} := \frac{((6^7) \times (0 - (1 - 4)))}{(((8 \times 9)^3) \times (5 - 2))} \\
 & := \frac{((67 + (0 - 1)) \times 4)}{(8 \times ((9 \times 3) - 5) \times 2)} := \frac{(6 - (7 \times (0 \times 14)))}{(8 - (9 \times (3 - (5 - 2))))} := \frac{(6 - (7 + (0 - (1 \times 4))))}{(8 + (9 - (3 + (5 \times 2))))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 \times ((7 - (0 - 1)) \times 4))}{(8 \times ((9 - 3) \times 5) + 2)} := \frac{(6 \times ((7 - (0 - 1))^4))}{8^{9+3-5-2}} := \frac{(6 \times ((7 + (0 - 1)) \times 4))}{((8 + (93 - 5)) \times 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(6 \times (7 - (0 - (1 \times 4))))}{((8 \times 9) + ((3 + 5) \times 2))} := \frac{(6 \times (7 - (0 - (1^4))))}{(8^{9+3-5 \times 2})} := \frac{(6 \times (7 - (0 - (1 + 4))))}{(8 + ((9 + 35) \times 2))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 \times (7 - (0 - (1 - 4))))}{(8 - (9 - (35 - 2)))} := \frac{(6 \times (7 - (0 \times 14)))}{(8 + ((9 + (3 \times 5)) \times 2))} := \frac{(6 \times (7 \times (0 + (1 \times 4))))}{(8 - (9 - ((3 \times 5)^2)))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 \times (7^{-01+4}))}{((8 + (9 - 3))^{5-2})} := \frac{(6 \times (7 + (0 - (1^4))))}{(8 - (9 + (3 - 52)))} := \frac{(6 \times (7 + (0 - (1 - 4))))}{((8 + ((9 \times 3) + 5)) \times 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(6 \times (70 - (1 + 4)))}{((8 + (9 + (3^5))) \times 2)} := \frac{(6 \times (70 - (1 - 4)))}{(8 \times (9 + ((3 + 5)^2)))} := \frac{(6 \times (70 \times (1^4)))}{(8 \times ((9 \times (3 + 5)) - 2))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 \times (70 + (1 \times 4)))}{(8 \times ((9 \times (3 + 5)) + 2))} := \frac{(6 \times (70 + 14))}{(8 \times (9 + (3 \times (5^2))))} := \frac{(6^{7+01^4})}{(8 \times ((9 - 3)^{5+2}))} \\
 & := \frac{(8 \times ((9 - 3)^{5-2}))}{(8 \times ((9 - 3)^{5-2}))} := \frac{(6^{7-01 \times 4})}{(6^{7-01 \times 4})} := \frac{(6 + ((7 + (0 - 1)) \times 4))}{(6 + ((7 + (0 - 1)) \times 4))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 + ((7 + (0 - 1))^4))}{(8 + ((9 + 3)^{5-2}))} := \frac{(6 + (7 - (0 - (1 + 4))))}{(8 \times (9 + (3^5-2)))} := \frac{(6 + (7 - (0 - 14)))}{(8 \times (9 + (3 - (5 + 2))))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 + (7 + (0 - (1 \times 4))))}{(8 - (9 - (3 + (5 \times 2))))} := \frac{(6 + (7 + (0 - (1^4))))}{(8 \times (9 - (3 + (5 - 2))))} := \frac{(6 + (70 - (1^4)))}{(8 - (9 - (35 + 2)))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 + (70 + (1 + 4)))}{(8 + (93 + (5 + 2)))} := \frac{(6 + (70 + 14))}{(8 \times (9 + (3 + (5 - 2))))} := \frac{(6 + 7014)}{((8 - (9 - 3)) \times 5)^2)} \\
 & := \frac{(67 \times (0 - (1 - 4)))}{(8 \times (9 \times 3)) + 52} := \frac{(670 + (1 + 4))}{((8 + ((9 \times 3) - 5))^2)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{73684}{92105} &:= \frac{(((7 \times 3) - 6) \times 8) - 4}{((9 + (2 \times 10)) \times 5)} := \frac{(((7 - (3 - 6)) \times 8) + 4)}{((9 + (2 + 10)) \times 5)} := \frac{(((7 \times 3) + 6) \times (8 + 4))}{((9^{2 \times 1 + 0}) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((7 + (3 + 6)) \times 8) + 4)}{((9 + 2) \times (10 + 5))} := \frac{(((7 + 3) \times 6) + (8 \times 4))}{((9 + 2) \times 10) + 5} := \frac{(((7 - 3) \times 6) + 84)}{9 \times ((2 \times 10) - 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 - (3 - (6 + 8))) \times 4)}{(9 \times (2 \times (1 \times (0 + 5))))} := \frac{((7 - (3 \times (6 - 8))) \times 4)}{((9 - 2) \times 10) - 5} := \frac{((7 - (3 + (6 - 8))) \times 4)}{(9 - (2 + (1 - 0))) \times 5} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 - (3 - 6)) \times (8 \times 4))}{(((9^2) - (1 - 0)) \times 5)} := \frac{((7 - (3 - 6)) \times (8 + 4))}{((9 + (21 - 0)) \times 5)} := \frac{((7 - (3 - 6)) \times (8 - 4))}{((9 + (2 - (1 - 0))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 \times 36) + (8 \times 4))}{(((9^2) - 10) \times 5)} := \frac{((7 + (3 + (6 - 8))) \times 4)}{((9 - (2 - (1 - 0))) \times 5)} := \frac{((7 + (3 + 6)) \times (8 - 4))}{((9^2) - (1^{05}))} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 + 3) \times ((6 \times 8) - 4))}{((9 + 2) \times (10 \times 5))} := \frac{((7 + 3) \times (6 \times (8 + 4)))}{(9 \times (2 \times (10 \times 5)))} := \frac{((7 + 3) \times (6 + (8 + 4)))}{9 \times ((2 \times 10) + 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 - (3 - ((6 + 8) \times 4)))}{((9^2) - (1 - (0 - 5)))} := \frac{(7 - (3 - (6 \times (8 + 4))))}{(((9 \times 2) + (1 - 0)) \times 5)} := \frac{(7 - (3 - (6 \times (8 - 4))))}{((9 - (2 \times (1 - 0))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 - (3 - (68 - 4)))}{((9 - (2 - 10)) \times 5)} := \frac{(7 \times ((3 - (6 - 8)) \times 4))}{((9 \times (2 \times 10)) - 5)} := \frac{(7 \times ((3 + 6) \times (8 + 4)))}{(9 \times (21 \times (0 + 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 \times (3 \times ((6 \times 8) - 4)))}{((9 + 2) \times 105)} := \frac{(7 \times (3 \times (6 \times (8 + 4))))}{(9 \times (2 \times 105))} := \frac{(7 \times (36 + (8 - 4)))}{((9 - 2) \times (10 \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + ((3^6) - (8 - 4)))}{((92 \times 10) - 5)} := \frac{(7 + ((3^6) + (8 - 4)))}{((92 \times 10) + 5)} := \frac{(7 + ((3^6) - 84))}{(((9^2) \times 10) + 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (3 - (6 - (8 \times 4))))}{(9 \times ((2 - (1 - 0)) \times 5))} := \frac{(7 + (3 - (6 - (8 - 4))))}{(9 + (2 - (1^{05})))} := \frac{(7 + (3 + (6 - (8 + 4))))}{(9 + (2 - (1 - (0 - 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(7 + (3 + (6 - (8 - 4))))}{(9 + (2 - (1 + (0 - 5))))} := \frac{(7 + (3 + (6 + (8 \times 4))))}{((9 + (2 + (1 - 0))) \times 5)} := \frac{(7 + (3 + (6 + (8 - 4))))}{(9 + (21 + (0 - 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{7368 + 4}{9210 + 5} := \frac{7368 - 4}{9210 - 5}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{9237}{461850} &:= \frac{(((9^2) \times 3) + 7)}{(4 \times ((6 - (1^8))^5 + 0))} := \frac{(((9^2) \times 3) - 7)}{(((4 \times 61) - 8) \times 50)} := \frac{(((9 + 2) \times 3) - 7)}{(4 + (6 \times (1 + (8 - (5 - 0))))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((9 - 2) \times 3) - 7)}{((4 - 6) \times ((1 - 8) \times 50))} := \frac{((9 - (2 + 3))^7)}{((4^{6+1^8}) \times 50)} := \frac{((9 - (2 - 3))^7)}{(((4 + (6 \times 1))^8) \times (5 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{((9 \times (2 \times 3)) - 7)}{((46 + (1^8)) \times 50)} := \frac{((9 \times (2 + 3)) + 7)}{(4 \times ((6 - (1 - 8)) \times 50))} := \frac{((9 \times (2 + 3)) - 7)}{((46 - (1 \times 8)) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{((9 \times 23) - 7)}{((4 + 6) \times (1 + (8 - (5 - 0))))} := \frac{((9^2) - (3 \times 7))}{(4 \times ((6 + (1 + 8)) \times 50))} := \frac{((9 + (2 - 3)) \times 7)}{(4 \times ((6 + (1 \times 8)) \times 50))} \\
 &:= \frac{((9 + 23) \times 7)}{(4 \times ((6 + 1) \times (8 \times 50)))} := \frac{(9 - ((2^3) - 7))}{(9 - ((2^3) - 7))} := \frac{(9 - ((2 - 3) \times 7))}{(9 - ((2 - 3) \times 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 - (2 - (3 \times 7)))}{((4 + (6 + 18)) \times 50)} := \frac{(9 - (2 - (3 - 7)))}{((4 + (6 + (1 - 8))) \times 50)} := \frac{(9 - (2 \times (3 - 7)))}{((4 + (6 - (1 - 8))) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 - (2 + (3 - 7)))}{((4 + (6 + (1^8))) \times 50)} := \frac{(9 - (2 - 37))}{((4 + ((6 - 1) \times 8)) \times 50)} := \frac{(9 \times (2 - (3 - 7)))}{((46 + (1 \times 8)) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 \times (2 \times (3 + 7)))}{((4 + 6) \times (18 \times 50))} := \frac{(9^{2^3-7})}{((4 + ((6 - (1^8))) \times 50)} := \frac{(9 + ((2^3) + 7))}{(4 \times (6 \times ((1^8) \times 50)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 + ((2^3) - 7))}{((4 + (6 \times (1^8))) \times 50)} := \frac{(9 + ((2 - 3) \times 7))}{(4 + (6 + (18 \times (5 - 0))))} := \frac{(9 + (2 - (3 - 7)))}{(((4 \times 6) - (1 + 8)) \times 50)} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 + (2 \times (3 + 7)))}{(((4 \times 6) + 1) \times (8 + 50))} := \frac{(9 + (2 \times (3 - 7)))}{(4 + (6 + (1 \times (8 \times (5 - 0))))))} := \frac{(9 + (2 + (3 \times 7)))}{(((4 \times (6 \times 1)) + 8) \times 50)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{(9 + (2 + (3 - 7)))}{((4 - (6 - (1 + 8))) \times 50)} & := \frac{(9 + (23 \times 7))}{((4 + (6 \times 1)) \times 850)} & := \frac{(9 + (23 + 7))}{((46 + (1 - 8)) \times 50)} \\ & := \frac{(9 + (23 - 7))}{(((4 \times 6) + (1^8)) \times 50)} & := \frac{(92 - (3 + 7))}{((4^6) + (1 + (8 - (5 - 0))))} & := \frac{(92 - (3 - 7))}{(4 \times ((6 + 18) \times 50))} \\ & := \frac{(92 + (3 - 7))}{((4 + (6 + 1)) \times (8 \times 50))} & := \frac{(92 - 37)}{((46 + (1 + 8)) \times 50)} \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{9423}{150768}$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{(((9 + 4)^2) + 3)}{(1 \times (((50 \times 7) - 6) \times 8))} & := \frac{((9 - (4 + 2)) \times 3)}{(1 \times ((5 - (0 - (7 + 6))) \times 8))} & := \frac{((9 \times (4 + 2)) - 3)}{(1 \times ((5 - (0 - 7)) \times 68))} \\ & := \frac{((9 \times 4) - (2 - 3))}{((150 - 76) \times 8)} & := \frac{((9^{4-2}) + 3)}{((1 - 5) \times (0 - (7 \times (6 \times 8))))} & := \frac{((9 + (4^2)) \times 3)}{(150 \times ((7 - 6) \times 8))} \\ & := \frac{((9 + 42) \times 3)}{((1 - (5 \times (0 - 7))) \times 68)} & := \frac{((9 - 4) \times (2 + 3))}{(1 \times (50 \times ((7 - 6) \times 8)))} & := \frac{((94 \times 2) + 3)}{(((1 + 507) \times 6) + 8)} \\ & := \frac{(9 - ((4 - 2) \times 3))}{((1 + (5 - (0 \times 76))) \times 8)} & := \frac{(9 - ((4 - 2)^3))}{((1 - (5 + ((0 \times 7) - 6))) \times 8)} & := \frac{(9 - (4 - (2 \times 3)))}{(((1 - 5) \times (0 - (7 \times 6))) + 8)} \\ & := \frac{(9 - (4 - (2^3)))}{(((1 - (5 \times (0 - 7))) \times 6) - 8)} & := \frac{(9 - (4 - (2 + 3)))}{(((1 - 5) \times (0 - (7 \times 6))) - 8)} & := \frac{(9 - (4 - (2 - 3)))}{(1 - (5 + (0 - (76 - 8))))} \\ & := \frac{(9 - (4 + (2 - 3)))}{((1 + (5 - ((0 \times 7) - 6))) \times 8)} & := \frac{(9 - (4 - 23))}{(((1 + (5 - 0)) \times 76) - 8)} & := \frac{(9 \times ((4^2) + 3))}{(1 \times ((50 + 7) \times (6 \times 8)))} \\ & := \frac{(9 \times (4 - (2 - 3)))}{(15 \times ((0 \times 7) + (6 \times 8)))} & := \frac{(9 \times (4 \times (2^3)))}{((1 + (5 - 0)) \times 768)} & := \frac{(9 \times (4 + (2^3)))}{((1 - (5 \times (0 - 7))) \times (6 \times 8))} \\ & := \frac{(9 + ((4^2) - 3))}{(1 \times ((50 \times 7) - (6 - 8)))} & := \frac{(9 + ((4 - 2) \times 3))}{((1 - ((5 \times (0 - 7)) + 6)) \times 8)} & := \frac{(9 + ((4 - 2)^3))}{(((1 + (50 - 7)) \times 6) + 8)} \\ & := \frac{(9 + (4 - (2 \times 3)))}{(1 + (50 - (7 - 68)))} & := \frac{(9 + (4 - (2^3)))}{(1 \times (5 - (0 - (7 + 68))))} & := \frac{(9 + (4 - (2 + 3)))}{(((15 - (0 - (7 - 6))) \times 8)} \\ & := \frac{(9 + (4 - (2 - 3)))}{(((1 - (5 \times (0 - 7))) \times 6) + 8)} & := \frac{(9 + (4 \times (2 \times 3)))}{((1 - (5 \times (0 - (7 + 6)))) \times 8)} & := \frac{(9 + (4 \times (2^3)))}{((1 + (5 - (0 - 76))) \times 8)} \\ & := \frac{(9 + (4 \times (2 + 3)))}{(((1 + (5 - 0)) \times 76) + 8)} & := \frac{(9 + (4 + (2 \times 3)))}{((1 - (5 + (0 - (7 \times 6)))) \times 8)} & := \frac{(9 + (4 + (2^3)))}{((1 - ((5 \times (0 - 7)) - 6)) \times 8)} \\ & := \frac{(9 + (4 + (2 + 3)))}{((1 + (5 - (0 \times 7))) \times (6 \times 8))} & := \frac{(9 + (4 + (2 - 3)))}{((1 - 5) \times ((0 \times 7) - (6 \times 8)))} & := \frac{(9 + (4 + 23))}{((1 - (5 + (0 - 76))) \times 8)} \\ & := \frac{(9 + (42 + 3))}{((150 - (7 \times 6)) \times 8)} & := \frac{(9 + (42 - 3))}{((1^5 + 0) \times 768)} \end{aligned}$$

3.38 39 Equivalent Blocks

► $\frac{16748}{20935}$

$$\begin{aligned} & := \frac{(((1 - (6 - 7)) \times 4) + 8)}{(2 + (0 - (9 \times (3 - 5))))} & := \frac{(((1 - (6 - 7))^4) \times 8)}{((20 + (9 + 3)) \times 5)} & := \frac{(((1^6) + 7) \times (4 \times 8))}{((2^{09-3}) \times 5)} \\ & := \frac{(((1 + (6 \times 7)) \times 4) + 8)}{((2 \times (0 - 9)) + (3^5))} & := \frac{(((1 + 6) \times (7 \times 4)) - 8)}{((20 \times (9 + 3)) - 5)} & := \frac{(((16 + 7) \times 4) - 8)}{(((2 \times (0 + 9)) + 3) \times 5)} \\ & := \frac{(((16 - 7) \times 4) - 8)}{((2 \times (0 \times 9)) + 35)} & := \frac{((1 - ((6 - 7) \times 4)) \times 8)}{(20 + ((9 - 3) \times 5))} & := \frac{((1 - (6 - 7)) \times 48)}{(2 \times (0 + ((9 + 3) \times 5)))} \\ & := \frac{((1^{674}) \times 8)}{(2 \times ((0 \times 93) + 5))} & := \frac{((1 + (6 + (7 - 4))) \times 8)}{(2 - (0 - (93 + 5)))} & := \frac{((1 + (67 - 4)) \times 8)}{(20 \times ((9 \times 3) + 5))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((1+6) \times (7 \times (4 \times 8)))}{(20 \times (93+5))} := \frac{((16 - (7-4)) \times 8)}{((20 + (9-3)) \times 5)} := \frac{((16 \times 7) + (4+8))}{(20 + (9 \times (3 \times 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (6 + (7 - (4 \times 8))))}{((2 - ((0 \times 9) - 3)) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 \times (((6+7) \times 4) + 8))}{(((2 \times (0+9)) - 3) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 \times ((6 - (7-4)) \times 8))}{(2 \times ((0 \times 9) + (3 \times 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 4)) + 8))}{(20 \times (9 - (3 - 5)))} := \frac{(1 \times ((6 \times 74) + 8))}{((20+93) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 \times ((6 \times 74) - 8))}{((20 \times (9 \times 3)) + 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((6 + (7 \times 4)) \times 8))}{(20 \times (9 + (3 + 5)))} := \frac{(1 \times ((6 + 7) \times (4 \times 8)))}{((2^{09}) + (3 + 5))} := \frac{(1 \times ((6 + 7) \times (4 + 8)))}{((20 \times 9) + (3 \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (6 \times (7 \times (4 + 8))))}{(2 \times (0 + (9 \times 35)))} := \frac{(1 \times (6^{7+4-8}))}{(2 \times (0 + (9 \times (3 \times 5))))} := \frac{(1 \times (6 + (74 - 8)))}{(2 - (0 - (93 - 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (6 - (7 - (4 \times 8))))}{((2 - (0 - (9 - 3))) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 + (6 - (7 - (4 + 8))))}{((2 \times (0 \times 9)) + (3 \times 5))} := \frac{(1 + (6 - (7 + (4 - 8))))}{((2 \times (0 \times 93)) + 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (6 - (7 - 48)))}{(2 \times (0 + ((9 - 3) \times 5)))} := \frac{(1 + (67 - (4 + 8)))}{((2 - (0 - (9 + 3))) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 + (67 + (4 \times 8)))}{((20 \times (9 - 3)) + 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(16 \times ((7 - 4) \times 8))}{(20 \times (9 + (3 \times 5)))} := \frac{(16 + (7 \times 48))}{((2 - (0 - (9 \times 3))) \times 5)} := \frac{(16 \times ((7 + 4) \times 8))}{(16 \times ((7 + 4) \times 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(16 \times ((7 - 4) \times 8))}{(20 \times (9 + (3 \times 5)))} := \frac{(16 + (7 \times 48))}{(20 \times ((9 \times 3) - 5))} := \frac{(16 + 748)}{(20 + 935)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{18630}{27945} := \frac{(((1^8) + 6) \times 30)}{((27 + (9 \times 4)) \times 5)} := \frac{((1^{86}) \times 30)}{(2 + (7 - (9 - 45)))} := \frac{((1^{86}) + (3 - 0))}{(2 - (7 + (9 - (4 \times 5))))}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((1^8) \times (6 \times 30))}{(27 \times (9 - (4 - 5)))} := \frac{((1^8) + (6 + (3 - 0)))}{(2 - (((7 - 9) \times 4) - 5))} := \frac{((1^8) + (63 - 0))}{(2 \times (7 + ((9 \times 4) + 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (8 + 6)) \times 30)}{(27 \times ((9 - 4) \times 5))} := \frac{((1 + 8) \times 630)}{((2 + 7) \times 945)} := \frac{((1 - 8) \times (6 - 30))}{(2 \times (7 \times (9 + (4 + 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((18 \times 6) + 30)}{((2 \times (7 + 94)) + 5)} := \frac{((18 - 6) \times 30)}{(((2 \times 7) + 94) \times 5)} := \frac{(1 - (8 - (6 + (3 - 0))))}{(2 - (7 - (9 + (4 - 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (8 - (63 - 0)))}{(2 - (7 - (94 - 5)))} := \frac{(1 \times ((8 \times 6) + 30))}{((2 \times (7 \times 9)) - (4 + 5))} := \frac{(1 \times ((8^6) \times (3 - 0)))}{((2^7) \times (9 \times (4^5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((8 + 6) \times (3 - 0)))}{(2 + (7 + (9 + 45)))} := \frac{(1 \times ((8 + 6) \times 30))}{(((2 \times 7) - 9)^4 + 5)} := \frac{(1 \times ((8 - 6) \times 30))}{(2 + (7 + (9 \times (4 + 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((8 - 6)^3 + 0))}{(2 + ((7 - (9 - 4)) \times 5))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (6 - (3 - 0))))}{(2 \times (7 - (9 - (4 \times 5))))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (6 \times (3 - 0))))}{(2 \times ((7 \times 9) + 45))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (6 + (3 - 0))))}{(2 + (7 + (94 + 5)))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (6 + 30)))}{(27 + (9 \times 45))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (63 - 0)))}{(2 \times (7 \times (9 + 45)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 + (6 \times (3 - 0))))}{((2^7) - (94 - 5))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 + (6 + 30)))}{(2 + ((7 \times 9) - (4 - 5)))} := \frac{(1 + (8 - (6 - (3 - 0))))}{(2 + (7 - (9 - (4 + 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (8 + (6 - (3 - 0))))}{(2 + (7 - (9 \times (4 - 5))))} := \frac{(1 + (8 + (6 + (3 - 0))))}{(2 + (7 + (9 + (4 + 5))))} := \frac{(1 + (86 - (3 - 0)))}{(2 + (79 + 45))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (86 + (3 - 0)))}{((2 \times (7 \times 9)) + (4 + 5))} := \frac{(18 \times (6 \times (3 - 0)))}{(27 \times (9 + (4 + 5)))} := \frac{(18 \times (6 \times 30))}{(27 \times (9 \times (4 \times 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(18 \times (6 + 30))}{(27 + 945)} := \frac{(18 + (6 \times 30))}{(2 + (((7 \times 9) - 4) \times 5))} := \frac{(18 + (6 + 30))}{((2 \times (7 + (9 \times 4))) - 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(186 \times (3 - 0))}{(27 \times ((9 \times 4) - 5))} := \frac{186 + 30}{279 + 45} := \frac{186 - 30}{279 - 45}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{20169}{53784} := \frac{(((2 - (0 - 1))^6) - 9)}{((53 + 7) \times (8 \times 4))} := \frac{(((2 \times (0 - 1)) + 6) \times 9)}{(((5 - 3)^7) - (8 \times 4))} := \frac{((2 - (0 - (1 + 6))) \times 9)}{((53 - (7 - 8)) \times 4)}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{((2 - (0 - 1)) \times (6 + 9))}{((5^3) + (7 - (8 + 4)))} := \frac{((2 - (0 - 1)) \times 69)}{((53 - 7) \times (8 + 4))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + (1 \times 6))) + 9)}{(53 + (7 - (8 - 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{((2^{01 \times 6}) \times 9)}{(((5 - 3)^7) \times (8 + 4))} := \frac{((2 + (0 - (1 - 6))) \times 9)}{((5 + 37) \times (8 - 4))} := \frac{((2 + (0 - 1)) \times (6 \times 9))}{(53 + (7 + 84))} \\
 & := \frac{((2 + (0 - 1)) \times (6^9))}{(((5 - (3 - 7)) \times 8)^4)} := \frac{((2 + (0 - 1)) \times (6 + 9))}{(5 \times (3 - (7 - (8 + 4))))} := \frac{((2 + (0 - 1)) \times 69)}{((53 - 7) \times (8 - 4))} \\
 & := \frac{((20 - (1 + 6)) \times 9)}{((5 + (3 \times 7)) \times (8 + 4))} := \frac{((20 - (1 - 6)) \times 9)}{(5 \times ((3 + 7) \times (8 + 4)))} := \frac{((20 \times (1 \times 6)) + 9)}{((5 + (3 + 78)) \times 4)} \\
 & := \frac{((20 + (1 \times 6)) \times 9)}{((5 - 3) \times (78 \times 4))} := \frac{((20 + (1 - 6)) \times 9)}{(5 \times ((3 + (7 + 8)) \times 4))} := \frac{((20 + 1) \times 69)}{((53 - 7) \times 84)} \\
 & := \frac{((201 - 6) \times 9)}{(5 \times (3 \times (78 \times 4)))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - ((1^6)^9)))}{((5 + (3 \times (7 - 8))) \times 4)} := \frac{(2 - (0 - ((1^6) + 9)))}{(5 + (3^{7-8+4}))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 - (0 - (1 - (6 - 9))))}{((5 \times (3 - (7 - 8))) - 4)} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (1 + (6 \times 9))))}{((53 - (7 + 8)) \times 4)} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (1 + (6 + 9))))}{(53 + (7 - (8 + 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 - (0 - (1 + 69)))}{(((5 + 3) \times 7) - 8) \times 4} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (16 + 9)))}{((5 + ((3 \times 7) - 8)) \times 4)} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (16 - 9)))}{((5 \times (3 - (7 - 8))) + 4)} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times (0 - ((1 - 6) \times 9)))}{((53 + 7) \times (8 - 4))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (1 \times (6 \times 9))))}{((5 - (3 - 7)) \times (8 \times 4))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (1 \times (6 + 9))))}{(5 - (3 \times (7 - (8 \times 4))))} \\
 & := \frac{(20 \times ((1^6) \times 9))}{((5 + (3 + 7)) \times (8 \times 4))} := \frac{(20 \times ((1 + 6) \times 9))}{(5 \times (3 \times (7 \times (8 \times 4))))} := \frac{(20 + (1 - (6 - 9)))}{((5 \times (3 - 7)) + 84)} \\
 & := \frac{(20 + (1 + (6 \times 9)))}{((5 + (3 \times (7 + 8))) \times 4)} := \frac{(20 + 169)}{(5 + 37) \times (8 + 4)} := \frac{(201 - (6 + 9))}{(((5^3) + (7 - 8)) \times 4)} \\
 & := \frac{(201 - (6 - 9))}{(((5 - 3)^7) + 8) \times 4} := \frac{(201 + (6 - 9))}{(((5^3) + 7) \times (8 - 4))} := \frac{(201 + 69)}{(53 + 7) \times (8 + 4)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► 73248
91560

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(((7 + (3^2)) \times 4) + 8)}{((9 + (1 + 5)) \times (6 - 0))} := \frac{((7 - (3 - (2 + 4))) \times 8)}{(((9 - 1) \times 5) + 60)} := \frac{((7 - (3 + (2 - 4))) \times 8)}{((9 + (1^5)) \times (6 - 0))} \\
 & := \frac{((7 \times 32) - (4 \times 8))}{((9 - (1 \times 5)) \times 60)} := \frac{((7 + ((3 + 2) \times 4)) \times 8)}{(9 \times (1 \times (5 \times (6 - 0))))} := \frac{((7 + ((3 - 2) \times 4)) \times 8)}{((9 + 1) \times (5 + (6 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{((7 + (3 - (2 + 4))) \times 8)}{(9 + (1 + (5 \times (6 - 0))))} := \frac{((7 + (3 \times (2 \times 4))) \times 8)}{(9 + (1 + (5 \times 60)))} := \frac{((7 + (3 \times 2)) \times (4 \times 8))}{((9 - 1) \times (5 + 60))} \\
 & := \frac{((7 + (3 \times 2)) \times (4 + 8))}{((9 \times 15) + 60)} := \frac{((7 + (3 + (2 \times 4))) \times 8)}{((9 - (1 + 5)) \times 60)} := \frac{((7 + (3 + (2 - 4))) \times 8)}{((9 - 1) \times (5 + 60))} \\
 & := \frac{((9 \times 15) + 60)}{((7 + (3 - 2)) \times 48)} := \frac{((7 + 3) \times ((2 + 4) \times 8))}{((9 + (1^5)) \times 60)} := \frac{(91 - (5 + (6 - 0)))}{((7 + 3) \times (2 \times (4 + 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{((9 - (1^5)) \times 60)}{((7 + 3) \times (24 \times 8))} := \frac{((7 + 32) \times (4 + 8))}{((9 + (1^5)) \times 60)} := \frac{((9 + (1 - 5)) \times 60)}{((73 - (2 \times 4)) \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{((9 - 1) \times (5 \times 60))}{((73 - (2^4)) \times 8)} := \frac{(9 \times (1 \times (5 + 60)))}{((73 + (2 \times 4)) \times 8)} := \frac{((9 + 1) \times (5 + 60))}{((73 + 2) \times (4 \times 8))} \\
 & := \frac{((73 - (2^4)) \times 8)}{(9 + (1 + 560))} := \frac{(9 \times (15 \times (6 - 0)))}{(9 + (1 + 560))} := \frac{((9 + 1) \times (5 \times 60))}{(9 + (1 + 560))} \\
 & := \frac{(7 - (3 - ((2^4) \times 8)))}{(9 + (156 - 0))} := \frac{(7 - (3 - ((2 + 4) \times 8)))}{(9 + (1 - (5 - 60)))} := \frac{(7 - (3 - (2 \times (4 + 8))))}{(91 - (56 - 0))} \\
 & := \frac{(7 - (3 - (24 + 8)))}{(9 + ((1 + 5) \times (6 - 0)))} := \frac{(7 \times ((3 \times 24) - 8))}{((9 + 1) \times (56 - 0))} := \frac{(7 \times ((3 - 2) \times (4 + 8)))}{((9 \times (1 \times 5)) + 60)} \\
 & := \frac{(7 \times (3 \times (24 \times 8)))}{(9 \times (1 \times 560))} := \frac{(7 \times (3 \times (24 + 8)))}{((9 + (1 \times 5)) \times 60)} := \frac{(7 + (((3 + 2)^4) - 8))}{((9 - (1 - 5)) \times 60)} \\
 & := \frac{(7 + (3 - (2 + (4 - 8))))}{(9 + ((1^5) \times (6 - 0)))} := \frac{(7 + (3 - (2 - 48)))}{(9 + ((1^5) + 60))} := \frac{(7 + (3 + (2 - (4 - 8))))}{(9 + (1 \times (5 + (6 - 0))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(7 + (3 + (2 + (4 + 8))))}{(9 + (15 + (6 - 0)))} := \frac{(7 + (3 + (2 + (4 - 8))))}{(9 - (1 \times (5 - (6 - 0))))} := \frac{(7 + (3 + (2 + 48)))}{(9 + (1 + (5 + 60)))} \\ &:= \frac{(732 - (4 + 8))}{((9 + (1 + 5)) \times 60)} := \frac{732 + 48}{915 + 60} := \frac{732 - 48}{915 - 60} \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{74108}{92635}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(((7 \times 4) - (1 - 0)) \times 8)}{(9 \times (2 \times ((6 - 3) \times 5)))} := \frac{(((7 \times 4) + 10) \times 8)}{((9 + ((2^6) + 3)) \times 5)} := \frac{(((7 \times 4) - 10) \times 8)}{(9 \times ((2 \times 6) + (3 + 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{((7 - (4 - (1 - 0))) \times 8)}{(9 + (2 - (6 - 35)))} := \frac{((7 - (4 \times (1 - 0))) \times 8)}{(9 - (2 - ((6 \times 3) + 5)))} := \frac{((7 - (4 + (1 - 0))) \times 8)}{(9 + (2 - (6 - (3 \times 5))))} \\ &:= \frac{((7 - (4 - 10)) \times 8)}{(9 + ((2 \times 63) - 5))} := \frac{((7 \times (4 \times 10)) + 8)}{(9 \times ((2^{6-3}) \times 5))} := \frac{((7 \times (4 \times (1 - 0))) + 8)}{(((9 \times 2) - (6 + 3)) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{((7 \times 4) + (10 \times 8))}{((9 + (2 \times (6 + 3))) \times 5)} := \frac{((7^{4-1+0}) \times 8)}{((92 + 6) \times 35)} := \frac{((7^4) - (1 + (0 - 8)))}{((92 - 6) \times 35)} \\ &:= \frac{((7 + (4 - (1 - 0))) \times 8)}{((9 + (2 + (6 + 3))) \times 5)} := \frac{((7 + (4 \times (1 - 0))) \times 8)}{(((9 + 26) \times 3) + 5)} := \frac{((7 + (4 + (1 - 0))) \times 8)}{(((9 + (2 - 6))^3) - 5)} \\ &:= \frac{((7 + (4 - 10)) \times 8)}{(9 + ((2 \times (6 - 3)) - 5))} := \frac{((7 + 4) \times 108)}{(((9^2) + (6^3)) \times 5)} := \frac{((7 - 4) \times 108)}{(9 \times ((2 \times 6) - 3) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{((74 + 10) \times 8)}{(((9 \times 2) + 6) \times 35)} := \frac{(7 - (4 - (1 - (0 - 8))))}{(9 - (2 - (6 - (3 - 5))))} := \frac{(7 \times ((4 \times 10) + 8))}{(((9^2) + (6 - 3)) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(7 \times ((4 + (1 - 0)) \times 8))}{((9 - (2 - 63)) \times 5)} := \frac{(9 + (2 \times (6 \times (3 + 5))))}{(7 \times (4 - (1 \times (0 - 8))))} := \frac{((9 \times (2 + 6)) + (3^5))}{(7 \times (4 \times (1 - (0 - 8))))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 \times (4 \times (1 \times (0 + 8))))}{((9 + 26) \times (3 + 5))} := \frac{(7 \times (4 \times (10 + 8)))}{(9 \times (2 + (63 + 5)))} := \frac{(7 \times (4 \times (10 - 8)))}{((9 + (2 + (6 - 3))) \times 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(7 \times (4 \times 108))}{(9 \times (2 \times (6 \times 35)))} := \frac{(7 \times (4 \times (1^{08})))}{(9 + (2 \times ((6 \times 3) - 5)))} := \frac{(7 \times (4 \times (10 - 8)))}{(9 + ((2 \times 63) + 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 \times (4 + (10 \times 8)))}{((9 + (2 \times 6)) \times 35)} := \frac{(7 + (4 + (1 - (0 - 8))))}{(9 + (2 \times (6 - (3 - 5))))} := \frac{(7 + (4 + (1 + (0 - 8))))}{(9 - (2 - (6 - (3 + 5))))} \\ &:= \frac{(7 + (41 - (0 \times 8)))}{((9^2) - (6 + (3 \times 5)))} := \frac{(7 + (41 + (0 - 8)))}{((9 - (2 - (6 - 3))) \times 5)} := \frac{(74 - (10 - 8))}{(9 \times (2 + (6 - (3 - 5))))} \\ &:= \frac{(74 \times (10 - 8))}{((9 \times (2 + (6 \times 3))) + 5)} := \frac{(74 + (10 + 8))}{(92 + ((6 \times 3) + 5))} := \frac{(74 + (10 - 8))}{((9^2) + (6 + (3 + 5)))} \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{9327}{186540}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(((9 + 3) \times 2) + 7)}{((1^8) - (6 - (5^4 + 0)))} := \frac{(((9 - 3) \times 2) - 7)}{(((18 - 6) \times 5) + 40)} := \frac{(((9 - 3)^2) - 7)}{((18 \times (6 \times 5)) + 40)} \\ &:= \frac{((9 - (3 + 2)) \times 7)}{(1 \times ((8 \times 65) + 40))} := \frac{((9 \times (3^2)) + 7)}{((1 + ((8 \times 6) - 5)) \times 40)} := \frac{((9 \times (3 + 2)) - 7)}{(1 \times ((8 + (6 + 5)) \times 40))} \\ &:= \frac{((9 \times 3) - (2 \times 7))}{((1^8) \times (65 \times (4 - 0)))} := \frac{((9 \times 3) - (2 - 7))}{((1 + (8 + (6 + (5^4 + 0))))} := \frac{((9 + (3 + 2)) \times 7)}{(((1 + 8) \times 6) - 5) \times 40)} \\ &:= \frac{((9 + (3 - 2)) \times 7)}{(((1^8) + 6) \times (5 \times 40))} := \frac{(9 + 3) \times 27}{((18 - 6) \times 540)} := \frac{(9 - 3) \times (2 + 7)}{(9 - 3) \times (2 + 7)} \\ &:= \frac{(9 - 3) \times 27}{(1 \times ((86 - 5) \times 40))} := \frac{(9 - ((3 - 2) \times 7))}{(1 \times (8 \times (6 - (5 - (4 - 0))))} := \frac{(9 - ((3 - 2)^7))}{((1 - (8 - (6 + 5))) \times 40)} \\ &:= \frac{(9 - (3 - (2 \times 7)))}{((1 + (8 + (6 - 5))) \times 40)} := \frac{(9 - (3 - (2 + 7)))}{((1 + (8 + 6)) \times (5 \times (4 - 0)))} := \frac{(9 - (3 - (2 - 7)))}{((1^{86}) \times (5 \times (4 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 - (3 \times (2 - 7)))}{(1 \times (8 \times (6 + (54 - 0))))} := \frac{(9 \times ((3 \times 2) + 7))}{((1 + 8) \times (65 \times (4 - 0)))} := \frac{(9 \times (3^2) - 7)}{(9 \times ((3^2) - 7))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 \times ((3 - 2) \times 7))}{(18 \times ((6 \times 5) + 40))} := \frac{(9 \times (3 \times (2 \times 7)))}{(1 \times ((8 + 6) \times 540))} := \frac{(9 \times (3 \times (2 + 7)))}{(18 \times (6 \times (5 + 40)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(9 \times (3 + (2 + 7)))}{(1 \times (8 \times (6 \times (5 + 40))))} := \frac{(9 \times 327)}{((1 + 8) \times 6540)} := \frac{(9^{3^2-7})}{((1 + (8 - 6)) \times 540)} \\
 & := \frac{(9 + ((3 \times 2) + 7))}{((1 + ((8 - 6) \times 5)) \times 40)} := \frac{(9 + ((3^2) + 7))}{((18 \times (6 \times 5)) - 40)} := \frac{(9 + ((3 - 2) \times 7))}{(1 \times (8 \times ((6 - 5) \times 40)))} \\
 & := \frac{(9 + ((3 - 2)^7))}{(1 \times (8 \times (65 - 40)))} := \frac{(9 + (3 - (2 + 7)))}{(1 + (8 + (6 + (5 + 40))))} := \frac{(9 + (3 \times (2 + 7)))}{(18 \times ((6 - 5) \times 40))} \\
 & := \frac{(9 + (3 + (2^7)))}{(1 \times ((8 + 6) \times (5 \times 40)))} := \frac{(9 + (3 + (2 - 7)))}{(1 \times (86 + (54 - 0)))} := \frac{(9 + (32 + 7))}{(1 \times (8 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 - 0)))))} \\
 & := \frac{(9 + (32 - 7))}{((18 - (6 - 5)) \times 40)} := \frac{(93 + 27)}{((18 - 6) \times (5 \times 40))} := \frac{(93 - 27)}{((1 + ((8 - 6)^5)) \times 40)}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.39 40 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{17352}{69408} & := \frac{(((1 + 7) \times (3^5)) + 2)}{((6^{9-4+0}) + 8)} := \frac{(((1 + 7) \times (3^5)) - 2)}{((6^{9-4+0}) - 8)} := \frac{((1 - (7 - 35)) \times 2)}{((69 - 40) \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{((1^{7^3}) \times 52)}{((6 \times (9 \times (4 - 0))) - 8)} := \frac{((1 + (7 - (3 - 5)))^2)}{(((6 \times 9) - (4 - 0)) \times 8)} := \frac{((1 + (7 + 3)) \times (5 \times 2))}{((6 + (9 + 40)) \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{((1 + (73 \times 5)) \times 2)}{((6 + (9 \times 40)) \times 8)} := \frac{((17 + 3) \times (5 \times 2))}{((6 + (94 - 0)) \times 8)} := \frac{((17 + 3) \times (5 - 2))}{(6 \times ((9 - (4 - 0)) \times 8))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (7 - (3 \times (5 \times 2))))}{((6 - 9) \times (4 \times (0 - 8)))} := \frac{(1 - (7 - (3 \times (5^2))))}{(69 \times (4 - (0 \times 8)))} := \frac{(1 - (7 - (3 \times (5 + 2))))}{((6 + 9) \times (4 - (0 \times 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (7 - (3 \times (5 - 2))))}{((6 - 9) \times (4 + (0 - 8)))} := \frac{(1 - (7 - (3 + (5^2))))}{((6 + (9 - (4 - 0))) \times 8)} := \frac{(1 - (7 - (35 - 2)))}{(6 + (94 - (0 - 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times ((7 \times (3 + 5)) - 2))}{(6 \times (9 \times (4 - (0 \times 8))))} := \frac{(1 \times ((7 + (3 - 5))^2))}{(6 + (94 - (0 \times 8)))} := \frac{(1 \times ((7 + 35) \times 2))}{((6 + (9 \times (4 - 0))) \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times ((73 + 5) \times 2))}{(6 \times ((9 + (4 - 0)) \times 8))} := \frac{(1 \times (7 - (3 - 52)))}{((6 \times (9 \times (4 - 0))) + 8)} := \frac{(1 \times (7 \times (3 + (5 - 2))))}{(6 \times ((9 \times (4 - 0)) - 8))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (7 + ((3 + 5) \times 2)))}{(6 + (94 + (0 - 8)))} := \frac{(1 \times (7 + (3 \times (5 + 2))))}{(((6 \times 9) - 40) \times 8)} := \frac{(1 \times (7 + (3 + (5 - 2))))}{(((6 + 9) \times (4 - 0)) - 8)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (73 - (5 + 2)))}{(6 \times ((9 \times (4 - 0)) + 8))} := \frac{(1 + ((7 \times 3) + 52))}{((6 - (9 - 40)) \times 8)} := \frac{(1 + (7 - (3 + (5 - 2))))}{((6 - (9 - (4 - 0))) \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (7 \times ((3 \times 5) + 2)))}{((6 + 9) \times (4 \times (0 + 8)))} := \frac{(1 + (7 \times (3 \times (5 + 2))))}{(((6 + 9) \times 40) - 8)} := \frac{(1 + (7 \times (3 + (5 + 2))))}{((69 \times (4 - 0)) + 8)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (7 + (3 \times (5 \times 2))))}{((6 + (9 + (4 - 0))) \times 8)} := \frac{(1 + (7 + (3 \times (5 - 2))))}{(((6 + 9) \times (4 - 0)) + 8)} := \frac{(1 + (7 + (3 + (5 - 2))))}{((6 - (9 + 4)) \times (0 - 8))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (7 + (35 + 2)))}{((6 + 9) \times (4 - (0 - 8)))} := \frac{(1 + (73 - (5 + 2)))}{((69 \times (4 - 0)) - 8)} := \frac{(17 \times (3 \times (5 - 2)))}{(6 \times (94 - (0 - 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{(173 + (5 + 2))}{((6 + 9) \times (40 + 8))} := \frac{(173 + (5 - 2))}{((6 - 94) \times (0 - 8))} := \frac{1735 + 2}{6940 + 8} \\
 & := \frac{1735 - 2}{6940 - 8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23517}{94068} & := \frac{(((2^3) + 5) \times 17)}{((9 + (4 - 0)) \times 68)} := \frac{((2 \times (3 + (5 \times 1))) + 7)}{(94 - (0 - (6 - 8)))} := \frac{((2^3) + (51 - 7))}{((9 \times (4 \times (0 + 6))) - 8)} \\
 & := \frac{((2 + 3) \times (5 \times (1 + 7)))}{((94 - (0 - 6)) \times 8)} := \frac{((2 + 3) \times (5 + (1 \times 7)))}{((9 - (4 - 0)) \times (6 \times 8))} := \frac{((2 + 3) \times (5 + 17))}{((9 + (40 + 6)) \times 8)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(23 \times (5 - 1)) - 7}{(9 - (4 - 0)) \times 68} := \frac{(2 - 35) \times (1 - 7)}{(9 \times (40 + (6 \times 8)))} := \frac{(2 - (3 - (5 \times 17)))}{(((9 \times (4 - 0)) + 6) \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{(2 - (3 - (5 + 17)))}{((9 \times (4 - 0)) + (6 \times 8))} := \frac{(2 - (3 \times (5 - 17)))}{((9 + (4 - (0 - 6))) \times 8)} := \frac{(2 - (3 + (5 - (1 + 7))))}{((9 \times (4 \times (0 \times 6))) + 8)} \\
 & := \frac{(2 - (3 + (5 - 17)))}{((9 \times (4 - (0 \times 6))) + 8)} := \frac{(2 \times ((3 \times (5 + 1)) - 7))}{((9 - (4 + (0 - 6))) \times 8)} := \frac{(2 \times ((3^5) - (1 - 7)))}{((9 + (40 \times 6)) \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times ((3 + (5 + 1)) \times 7))}{(9 \times (4 \times (0 + (6 + 8))))} := \frac{(2 \times (3 \times (5 - (1^7))))}{(94 + (0 - (6 - 8)))} := \frac{(2 \times (3 \times (5 - (1 - 7))))}{((9 - (4 \times (0 - 6))) \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times (3 \times (5 + (1 \times 7))))}{(9 \times ((4 \times (0 + 6)) + 8))} := \frac{(2 \times (3 \times (5 + (1^7))))}{(9 \times (4^{-06+8}))} := \frac{(2 \times (3 \times (5 + (1 + 7))))}{((9 \times 40) - (6 \times 8))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times (3^{5-1^7}))}{(9 \times (4 - (0 - 68)))} := \frac{(2 \times (3 + (5 - (1^7))))}{((9 + (4 + (0 - 6))) \times 8)} := \frac{(2 \times (3 + (5 \times (1 + 7))))}{((9 + (40 - 6)) \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{(2 \times (3 + (5 \times 17)))}{((94 + (0 - 6)) \times 8)} := \frac{(2 \times (3 + (5 + (1^7))))}{(9 \times (4 \times (0 - (6 - 8))))} := \frac{(2 \times (35 - (1 \times 7)))}{((9 \times (4 \times (0 + 6))) + 8)} \\
 & := \frac{(2 + ((3^{5 \times 1}) + 7))}{(940 + 68)} := \frac{(2 + (3 - (5 - (1 \times 7))))}{((9 \times (4 - (0 \times 6))) - 8)} := \frac{(2 + (3 \times (5 \times (1 \times 7))))}{((9 \times 40) + 68)} \\
 & := \frac{(2 + (3 \times (5 + (1^7))))}{(94 + (0 - (6 + 8)))} := \frac{(2 + (3 + ((5 + 1) \times 7)))}{(94 \times (0 - (6 - 8)))} := \frac{(2 + (3 + (5 - (1^7))))}{(9 \times (4 - (0 \times 68)))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 + (3 + (5 \times (1^7))))}{((9 - (4 - (0 \times 6))) \times 8)} := \frac{(2 + (3 + (5 + 17)))}{(9 \times (4 - ((0 \times 6) - 8)))} := \frac{(2 + (3 + 517))}{(9 \times ((40 \times 6) - 8))} \\
 & := \frac{(2 + (35 \times (1 \times 7)))}{(940 + (6 \times 8))} := \frac{(23 - (5 - (1 + 7)))}{((9 + (4 - (0 \times 6))) \times 8)} := \frac{235 + 1 + 7}{9 \times (40 + 68)} \\
 & := \frac{235 - 17}{940 - 68}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.40 41 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{7932}{158640} & := \frac{(((7 + 9) \times 3) + 2)}{(1 \times ((5^{8-6}) \times 40))} := \frac{(((7 + 9)^3) \times 2)}{(((1 - (5 - 8))^6) \times 40)} := \frac{((7 - (9 - 3)) \times 2)}{(1 \times (5 \times ((8 - 6) \times (4 - 0))))} \\
 & := \frac{((7 - (9 - 3))^2)}{(((1 - (5 - 8)) \times 6) - (4 - 0))} := \frac{((7 \times (9 + 3)) + 2)}{(1 \times (5 \times (86 \times (4 - 0))))} := \frac{((7 \times (9 - 3)) - 2)}{((1 + (5 + (8 + 6))) \times 40)} \\
 & := \frac{((7 \times 9) - (3^2))}{(15 \times (8 + (64 - 0)))} := \frac{((7 \times 9) - (3 + 2))}{((15 + (8 + 6)) \times 40)} := \frac{((7 \times 9) - (3 - 2))}{(1 \times (5 \times (8 + (6 \times 40))))} \\
 & := \frac{((7 \times 9) + (3^2))}{(((1 + 5)^{8-6}) \times 40)} := \frac{((7^9-3) \times 2)}{(((15 - 8)^6) \times 40)} := \frac{((7 + (9 \times 3)) \times 2)}{(1 \times (((5 \times 8) - 6) \times 40))} \\
 & := \frac{((7 + (9 + 3)) \times 2)}{(1 \times ((5 + (8 + 6)) \times 40))} := \frac{((7 + (9 - 3)) \times 2)}{((15 - (8 - 6)) \times 40)} := \frac{((7 + 9) \times (3 \times 2))}{(((1^5) \times (8 \times (6 \times 40))))} \\
 & := \frac{((7 + 9) \times (3^2))}{(15 \times (8 \times (6 \times (4 - 0))))} := \frac{((79 + 3) \times 2)}{((1 - (5 - 86)) \times 40)} := \frac{(7 - (9 - (3 \times 2)))}{(1 \times (5 \times (8 \times (6 - (4 - 0)))))} \\
 & := \frac{(7 - (9 - (3^2)))}{((1 + (5 + 8)) \times (6 + (4 - 0)))} := \frac{(7 - (9 - (3 + 2)))}{((1 + (5 + (8 + (6 + 40)))))} := \frac{(7 - (9 - 32))}{(((1^5) + (8 + 6)) \times 40)} \\
 & := \frac{(7 \times ((9 + 3) \times 2))}{((1 + (5 + 8)) \times (6 \times 40))} := \frac{(7 \times ((9 - 3) \times 2))}{((15 - 8) \times (6 \times 40))} := \frac{(7 \times ((9 - 3)^2))}{(((15 \times 8) + 6) \times 40)} \\
 & := \frac{(7 \times (9 - (3 + 2)))}{(((1^5) \times ((8 + 6) \times 40))} := \frac{(7 \times (9 + (3^2)))}{((15 + (8 \times 6)) \times 40)} := \frac{(7 \times (9 + (3 + 2)))}{(((1^5) + (8 \times 6)) \times 40)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(7 \times (9 + (3 - 2)))}{((1 + ((5 \times 8) - 6)) \times 40)} & := \frac{(7 + ((9 \times 3)^2))}{((15 + 8) \times 640)} & := \frac{(7 + ((9 \times 3) - 2))}{(((1^5)^8) \times 640)} \\
 & := \frac{(7 + ((9 - 3)^2))}{(1 - (5 - (864 - 0)))} & := \frac{(7 + (9 - (3 \times 2)))}{(1 \times ((5 \times (8 \times 6)) - 40))} & := \frac{(7 + (9 - (3 + 2)))}{(1 \times (5 \times ((8 \times 6) - (4 - 0))))} \\
 & := \frac{(7 + (9 \times (3^2)))}{((1 - (5 - (8 \times 6))) \times 40)} & := \frac{(7 + (9 \times (3 + 2)))}{((1 + (5^{8-6})) \times 40)} & := \frac{(7 + (9 \times (3 - 2)))}{(1 \times (5 \times (8^{6-4+0})))} \\
 & := \frac{(7 + (9 + (3 \times 2)))}{((1 + (5 \times (8 - 6))) \times 40)} & := \frac{(7 + (9 + (3 - 2)))}{(1 - (5 - (86 \times (4 - 0))))} & := \frac{(7 + (9 + 32))}{(1 \times (5 \times (8 \times (6 \times (4 - 0)))))} \\
 & := \frac{(79 \times (3 - 2))}{(158 \times (6 + (4 - 0)))} & := \frac{(79 + (3 - 2))}{(1 \times ((5 \times 8)^{6-4+0}))} &
 \end{aligned}$$

3.41 42 Equivalent Blocks

▶ $\frac{20986}{73451} := \frac{(((2 - (0 - 9)) \times 8) - 6)}{((73 \times 4) - (5 \times 1))} := \frac{(((2 \times (0 + 9)) - 8) \times 6)}{(7 \times (3 \times (4 + (5 + 1))))} := \frac{((2 - (0 - (9 - 8))) \times 6)}{(73 - (4 + (5 + 1)))}$

$:= \frac{((2 \times (0 - (9 - 8))) + 6)}{(7 \times (3 + (4 - (5 \times 1))))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 \times 9)) + (8 \times 6))}{(7 \times (3 \times (4 + (5 - 1))))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 \times 98)) + 6)}{(7 \times (3 - (4 - (5 - 1))))}$

$:= \frac{((2 \times (0 + (9 \times 8))) + 6)}{(7 \times ((3^4) - (5 + 1)))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + 9)) - (8 - 6))}{(7 + (3 + (45 + 1)))} := \frac{((2^{0 \times 9 + 8}) \times 6)}{(7 \times (3 \times (4^{5-1})))}$

$:= \frac{((2^{09}) \times (8 \times 6))}{(7 \times (3 \times (4^{5+1})))} := \frac{((20 + (9 - 8)) \times 6)}{(7 \times (3 \times ((4 \times 5) + 1)))} := \frac{((20 + 9) \times (8 - 6))}{(7 \times (34 - (5 \times 1)))}$

$:= \frac{(2 - ((0 \times 9) - 86))}{((73 + 4) \times (5 - 1))} := \frac{(2 - ((0 \times 98) - 6))}{(7 \times (3 - (4 - (5 \times 1))))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - ((9 \times 8) + 6)))}{(7 \times (34 + (5 + 1)))}$

$:= \frac{(2 - (0 - ((9 \times 8) - 6)))}{(7 \times (((3 + 4) \times 5) - 1))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - ((9 + 8) \times 6)))}{(7 + ((3 + 4) \times 51))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (9 \times (8 - 6))))}{(7 + (3 \times ((4 \times 5) + 1)))}$

$:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (98 - 6)))}{(7 \times (3 + (45 - 1)))} := \frac{(2 - (0 \times (9 - 86)))}{(7 - (3 \times (4 - (5 - 1))))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - 986))}{(7 + 3451)}$

$:= \frac{(2 \times ((0 \times 9) + (8 \times 6)))}{(7 \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 - 1))))} := \frac{(2 \times ((0 \times 9) + 86))}{(7 \times ((3^4) + (5 \times 1)))} := \frac{(2 \times ((0 \times 98) + 6))}{(7 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 1)))}$

$:= \frac{(2 \times (0 - (9 - (8 \times 6))))}{(7 \times (34 + (5 \times 1)))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 - (9 - (8 + 6))))}{(7 \times (3 - (4 - (5 + 1))))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 - (9 - 86)))}{(7 \times ((3^4) - (5 - 1)))}$

$:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + ((9 \times 8) - 6)))}{((73 + 4) \times (5 + 1))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + ((9 + 8) \times 6)))}{((7 + (3 + 4)) \times 51)} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (9 - (8 - 6))))}{(7^{3+4-5 \times 1})}$

$:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (9 \times (8 - 6))))}{(7 \times ((3 \times 4) + (5 + 1)))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (9 + (8 \times 6))))}{(7 \times (3 \times ((4 \times 5) - 1)))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (9 + (8 + 6))))}{(7 \times (3 + (4 \times (5 \times 1))))}$

$:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (9 + (8 - 6))))}{(7 \times (3 + (4 + (5 - 1))))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (98 + 6)))}{(734 - (5 + 1))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (9 + (8 - 6))))}{(7 \times ((3 \times 4) + (5 - 1)))}$

$:= \frac{(20 \times ((9 - 8) \times 6))}{(7 \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 1))))} := \frac{(20 + ((9 \times 8) + 6))}{(20 + ((9 \times 8) + 6))} := \frac{(20 + ((9 + 8) \times 6))}{(20 + ((9 + 8) \times 6))}$

$:= \frac{(20 + ((9 - 8) \times 6))}{(7 \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 1))))} := \frac{(20 + (9 \times (8 - 6)))}{(7^{3-4+5-1})} := \frac{(209 \times (8 + 6))}{(7 \times ((3 \times (4 \times 5)) + 1))}$

$:= \frac{(20 + ((9 - 8) \times 6))}{(7 \times (3 + (4 + (5 + 1))))} := \frac{(20 + (9 \times (8 - 6)))}{(7 \times (3 + (4 \times (5 - 1))))} := \frac{(209 \times (8 + 6))}{(((7 + 3) \times (4^5)) + 1)}$

▶ $\frac{30618}{45927} := \frac{((3 - ((0 \times 6) - 1)) \times 8)}{(4 - (5 - ((9 - 2) \times 7)))} := \frac{((3 - (0 - (6 + 1))) \times 8)}{(4 \times (5 + ((9 \times 2) + 7)))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 + (6 \times 1))) + 8)}{(4 + (((5 + 9) \times 2) + 7))}$

$:= \frac{((30 - (6 \times 1)) \times 8)}{(4 \times ((5 \times 9) + 27))} := \frac{((30 \times (6 - 1)) + 8)}{((4 \times (59 + 2)) - 7)} := \frac{((30 \times (6 - 1)) - 8)}{((4 \times (5 \times (9 + 2))) - 7)}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(30 \times 6) + 18}{((4 \times 5) - 9) \times 27} & := \frac{((30 + (6 \times 1)) \times 8)}{(459 - 27)} & := \frac{((30 + (6 + 1)) \times 8)}{(4 + (5 \times ((9^2) + 7)))} \\
 & := \frac{((30 - 6) \times (1 + 8))}{((45 - 9) \times (2 + 7))} & := \frac{(3 - ((0 \times 6) - (1 + 8)))}{(4 - ((5 - (9 - 2)) \times 7))} & := \frac{(3 - (0 - (6 - (1 - 8))))}{(4 + (5 \times (9 + (2 - 7))))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 - (0 - (6 + (1^8))))}{((4 \times 5) + (9 - (2 \times 7)))} & := \frac{(3 - (0 - (6 + (1 - 8))))}{(4 - (5 - (9 + (2 - 7))))} & := \frac{(3 - (0 - (61 - 8)))}{(4 - (5 - (92 - 7)))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 \times ((0 \times 6) + 18))}{(45 + (9 + 27))} & := \frac{(3 \times ((0 \times 61) + 8))}{(4 \times (5 + (9 + (2 - 7))))} & := \frac{(3 \times (0 - (6 \times (1 - 8))))}{((4 + (5 + (9 \times 2))) \times 7)} \\
 & := \frac{(3 \times (0 - (6 - 18)))}{(4 + (5 - (9 \times (2 - 7))))} & := \frac{(3 \times (0 + ((6 + 1) \times 8))}{(3 \times (0 + ((6 - 1) \times 8)))} & := \frac{(3 \times (0 + ((6 - 1) \times 8))}{(4 \times (59 - (2 \times 7)))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (6 \times (1 \times 8))))}{(4 \times (5 + ((9 - 2) \times 7))} & := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (6 \times 18))}{((4 + (5 + 9)) \times 27)} & := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (6 \times (1^8))))}{(4 + (5 - (9 - 27)))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (6 + (1 \times 8))))}{(4 + ((5 \times 9) + (2 \times 7))} & := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (6 + 18))}{(4 + (5 + (92 + 7))} & := \frac{(3 + (0 - (6 - (1 + 8))))}{(4 + (5 - (9 - (2 + 7))))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 + (0 - (6 + (1 - 8))))}{((4 \times 5) - (9 - (2 - 7)))} & := \frac{(30 \times ((6 + 1) \times 8))}{(4 \times (5 \times (9 \times (2 \times 7))))} & := \frac{(30 \times (6 - (1^8)))}{((4 + 5) \times ((9 \times 2) + 7))} \\
 & := \frac{(30 \times (6 \times 18))}{(4 \times (5 \times (9 \times 27)))} & := \frac{(30 \times (6 + (1 \times 8))}{((4 + (5 + (9^2))) \times 7)} & := \frac{(30 + ((6 + 1) \times 8))}{(4 + (5 \times ((9 \times 2) + 7)))} \\
 & := \frac{(30 + ((6 - 1) \times 8))}{((4 \times ((5 + 9) \times 2)) - 7)} & := \frac{(30 + (6 - (1 \times 8))}{((4 - (5 - (9 - 2))) \times 7)} & := \frac{(30 + (6 \times (1 + 8))}{(45 + (9 \times (2 + 7)))} \\
 & := \frac{(30 + (6 \times 18))}{(4 + ((5 + 9)^2) + 7)} & := \frac{(30 + (6 + (1 \times 8))}{(4 + ((5 \times (9 + 2)) + 7))} & := \frac{(30 + (61 \times 8))}{((4 \times ((5 + 9)^2)) - 7)} \\
 & := \frac{(30 + 618)}{(45 + 927)} & := \frac{(306 \times (1 + 8))}{(459 \times (2 + 7))} & := \frac{(306 + (1 \times 8))}{(4 + ((5 \times 92) + 7))}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.42 43 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{16794}{50382} & := \frac{(((1 - (6 - 7)) \times 9) + 4)}{(5 + (0 - (3 - (8^2))))} & := \frac{(((1 - (6 \times (7 - 9))) \times 4)}{((50 \times 3) + (8 - 2))} & := \frac{(((1 - (6 - 7)) \times (9 - 4))}{(5 + ((0 - (3 - 8))^2))} \\
 & := \frac{((1^6) \times ((7 + 9) \times 4))}{((5 \times (0 + 38)) + 2)} & := \frac{((1^6) \times (7 - (9 - 4)))}{((5 \times (0 \times 3)) + (8 - 2))} & := \frac{((1^6) \times (7 + (9 \times 4)))}{(50 - (3 - 82))} \\
 & := \frac{((1^6) + ((7 \times 9) - 4))}{(5 \times (0 + (38 - 2)))} & := \frac{((1^6) + (7 + (9 + 4)))}{(50 + (3 + (8 + 2)))} & := \frac{((1 + (6 + (7 - 9))) \times 4)}{(50 - ((3 - 8) \times 2))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - ((6 - 7) \times (9 - 4)))}{(5 - (0 - (3 + (8 + 2))))} & := \frac{(1 - (6 - (7 \times (9 + 4))))}{(((5 + (0 - 3))^8) + 2)} & := \frac{(1 - (6 - (7 \times (9 - 4))))}{(5 - (0 - (3 + 82)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (6 - (7 + (9 + 4))))}{(5 \times (0 + (3 + (8 - 2))))} & := \frac{(1 - (6 - (7 + (9 - 4))))}{((5 \times (0 + 3)) + (8 - 2))} & := \frac{(1 - (6 - (79 + 4)))}{(((5^03) - 8) \times 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (6 + ((7 - 9) \times 4)))}{((5 \times (0 + 3)) - (8 - 2))} & := \frac{(1 - (6 + (7 - (9 \times 4))))}{(5 - (0 - (3 + (8^2))))} & := \frac{(1 - (67 - 94))}{(5 + (0 - (3 - 82)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times ((6 \times 7) - (9 + 4)))}{(5 - ((0 \times 3) - 82))} & := \frac{(1 \times ((6 \times 7) + (9 - 4)))}{((5^03) + (8 \times 2))} & := \frac{(1 \times ((6 + (7 - 9)) \times 4))}{((5 - (0 - 3)) \times (8 - 2))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (6 - ((7 - 9) \times 4)))}{((5 \times ((0 \times 3) + 8)) + 2)} & := \frac{(1 \times (6 - (7 - (9 - 4))))}{(5 + (0 - (3 - (8 + 2))))} & := \frac{(1 \times (6 \times (79 + 4)))}{(50 + (38^2))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (6 + (7 - (9 - 4))))}{(5 - (0 - (3 + (8 \times 2))))} & := \frac{(1 \times (6 + (7 + (9 + 4))))}{((50 - (3 + 8)) \times 2)} & := \frac{(1 \times (6 + 794))}{(50 \times (3 \times (8 \times 2)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (67 + (9 + 4)))}{(5 \times (0 + (3 \times (8 \times 2))))} & := \frac{(1 \times (679 - 4))}{((50 + (3 - 8))^2)} & := \frac{(1^{6794})}{(5 + ((0 \times 38) - 2))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(1 + ((6 \times 7) + (9 - 4)))}{((50 - 38)^2)} := \frac{(1 + ((67 \times 9) - 4))}{(50 \times (38 - 2))} := \frac{(1 + (6 - (7 - (9 - 4))))}{(5 \times (0 - (3 - (8 - 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (6 - (7 - 94)))}{((50 - 3) \times (8 - 2))} := \frac{(1 + (6^{7-9+4}))}{(50 - (3 - (8^2)))} := \frac{(1 + (6 + (7 - (9 - 4))))}{((5 \times (0 - (3 - 8))) + 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (6 + (7 \times (9 - 4))))}{(5 - (0 - ((3 + 8)^2)))} := \frac{(1 + (6 + (7 + (9 \times 4))))}{(5 \times (0 + (3 \times (8 + 2))))} := \frac{(1 + (6 + (7 + (9 + 4))))}{(5 - (0 - (38 \times 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (6 + (7 + (9 - 4))))}{((5 \times (0 + (3 + 8))) + 2)} := \frac{(1 + (67 - (9 - 4)))}{((5^{03}) + (8^2))} := \frac{(16 - (7 - (9 \times 4)))}{((5^{03}) + (8 + 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(16 \times (7 + (9 + 4)))}{(5 \times (0 + (3 \times (8^2))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{63284}{79105}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((6 + 3)^2) + 8) \times 4}{((79 + 10) \times 5)} := \frac{(((6 \times 3^2) + 8) \times 4)}{(((7 \times 9) - (1 - 0)) \times 5)} := \frac{(((6 \times 3)^2) - (8 - 4))}{((79 + (1 - 0)) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((6 \times 3) + 2) \times (8 \times 4))}{((7 + 9) \times (10 \times 5))} := \frac{(((6 \times 3) - 2) \times (8 - 4))}{((7 + (9 \times (1 - 0))) \times 5)} := \frac{(((6 \times 3) - 2) \times 84)}{((7 + 9) \times 105)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((6 + (3 - 2))^8) \times 4)}{((7^{9-1+0}) \times 5)} := \frac{((6 - (3 - (2 + 8))) \times 4)}{((7 \times (9 + (1 - 0))) - 5)} := \frac{((6 - (3 + 2)) \times (8 - 4))}{((7 - (9 - 1)) \times (0 - 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 - (3 - 28)) \times 4)}{(((7 + 9) \times 10) - 5)} := \frac{((6 \times (3 \times (2 \times 8))) + 4)}{(((7 \times 9) + 10) \times 5)} := \frac{((6 \times (3 \times 2)) + (8 \times 4))}{(((7 + (9 + (1 - 0))) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 \times (3 \times 28)) + 4)}{((7 \times (9 \times 10)) + 5)} := \frac{((6 \times (3 \times 28)) - 4)}{(((7 \times 9) + 10) \times 5)} := \frac{((6 \times 32) + (8 \times 4))}{((6 \times 32) + (8 \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 \times 32) + 84)}{((79 - 10) \times 5)} := \frac{((6^3) - (28 \times 4))}{((7 + (9 + 10)) \times 5)} := \frac{((6^3) + ((2^8) + 4))}{(7 \times ((9 \times 10) - 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6^3) + (2 \times (8 \times 4)))}{(7 \times ((9 + (1 - 0)) \times 5))} := \frac{((6 + ((3 \times 2) - 8))^4)}{(((7 \times 9) + (1 - 0)) \times 5)} := \frac{((6 + ((3 - 2) \times 8)) \times 4)}{(7 \times (9 + (1^{05})))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 + (3 - (2 - 8))) \times 4)}{((7 + (9 - (1 - 0))) \times 5)} := \frac{((6 + (3 + 2)) \times (8 + 4))}{(((7 + 9) \times 10) + 5)} := \frac{((6 + (3 - 2)) \times (8 + 4))}{(7 \times (9 + (1 - (0 - 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((63 - (2 + 8)) \times 4)}{(((7 \times 9) - 10) \times 5)} := \frac{((63 + (2 \times 8)) \times 4)}{(79 \times (1 \times (0 + 5)))} := \frac{((63 - 2) \times 84)}{(7 \times (910 + 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 - ((3 \times (2 - 8)) - 4))}{(7 \times (9 + (1 + (0 - 5))))} := \frac{(6 - (3 \times (2 - (8 - 4))))}{(7 + (9 - (1^{05})))} := \frac{(6 - (3 \times (2 - 84)))}{(7 \times (9 \times (1 \times (0 + 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (((3 \times 2) + 8) \times 4))}{((7 - 91) \times (0 - 5))} := \frac{((79 - (1 - 0)) \times 5)}{(6 + ((3 \times (2 + 8)) - 4))} := \frac{(6 \times ((3 + 2) \times 84))}{(7 \times (9 \times (10 \times 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times ((3 - 2) \times (8 \times 4)))}{((7 + 9) \times (10 + 5))} := \frac{((7 - (9 - 10)) \times 5)}{(6 + ((3 \times (2 + 8)) - 4))} := \frac{(6 + ((3 \times 2) - (8 - 4)))}{(7 + (9 - (1 - (0 - 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 + ((3 \times 2) + (8 - 4)))}{(7 + (9 - (1 + (0 - 5))))} := \frac{(6 + (3 \times (2 + (8 - 4))))}{((7 + (9 - 10)) \times 5)} := \frac{(63 \times ((2 \times 8) - 4))}{(7 \times (9 \times (10 + 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(632 - (8 - 4))}{((79 \times 10) - 5)} := \frac{(632 + (8 - 4))}{((79 \times 10) + 5)} := \frac{6328 + 4}{7910 + 5} \\
 &:= \frac{6328 - 4}{7910 - 5}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{7263}{108945}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((7 \times 2) + 6) \times 3)}{(1 - (0 - (894 + 5)))} := \frac{(((7 \times 2) - 6) \times 3)}{((1 - (0 - (8 + 9))) \times (4 \times 5))} := \frac{(((7^2) \times 6) + 3)}{((10 + 89) \times 45)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((7 + 2) \times 6) - 3)}{(1 \times (0 + ((8 + 9) \times 45)))} := \frac{(((7 - (2 - 6)) \times 3)}{((10 - (8 - 9)) \times 45)} := \frac{(((7 \times (2 \times 6)) - 3)}{((10 + (8 + 9)) \times 45)} \\
 &:= \frac{((7 \times 2) - (6 + 3))}{(10 + ((8 + (9 - 4)) \times 5))} := \frac{((7 \times 2) + (6 \times 3))}{((10 - (8 - 94)) \times 5)} := \frac{((7^2) - (6 - 3))}{(10 \times (89 - (4 \times 5)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(7^2) + (6 \times 3)}{((10^{8-9+4}) + 5)} & := \frac{((7^2) + (6 + 3))}{((10 \times 89) - (4 \times 5))} & := \frac{((7 + (2 \times 6)) \times 3)}{((10 \times (89 - 4)) + 5)} \\
 & := \frac{((7 + (2^6)) \times 3)}{(((10 \times 8) - 9) \times 45)} & := \frac{((7 + (2 + 6)) \times 3)}{((10 \times ((8 + 9) \times 4)) - 5)} & := \frac{((7 + (2 - 6)) \times 3)}{(1 - (0 - (89 + 45)))} \\
 & := \frac{((7 + 2) \times (6 \times 3))}{(10 \times ((8 - (9 - 4))^5))} & := \frac{((7 + 2) \times 63)}{((1 - (0 - 8)) \times 945)} & := \frac{((72 + 6) \times 3)}{(10 \times ((89 \times 4) - 5))} \\
 & := \frac{(7 - (2 - (6 \times 3)))}{((1 - (0 - ((8 + 9) \times 4))) \times 5)} & := \frac{(7 - (2 - (6 + 3)))}{(10 + (8 \times ((9 - 4) \times 5)))} & := \frac{(7 - (2 \times (6 - 3)))}{(1 \times (0 + ((8 - (9 - 4)) \times 5)))} \\
 & := \frac{(7 - (2 + (6 - 3)))}{((1 + (0 - (8 - (9 + 4)))) \times 5)} & := \frac{(7 \times ((2 \times 6) - 3))}{((10^8) \times 945)} & := \frac{(7 \times (2 \times (6 + 3)))}{((10 - 8) \times 945)} \\
 & := \frac{(7 \times (2 \times (6 - 3)))}{(10 \times (((8 + 9) \times 4) - 5))} & := \frac{(7 \times (2 + (6 - 3)))}{((1 - (0 - (8 \times (9 + 4)))) \times 5)} & := \frac{(7 + ((2 \times 6) + 3))}{(10 \times (8 + ((9 - 4) \times 5)))} \\
 & := \frac{(7 + ((2 + 6) \times 3))}{(1 \times (0 + ((89 + 4) \times 5)))} & := \frac{(7 + (2 - (6 - 3)))}{(1 - (0 - (8 + (9 \times (4 + 5))))))} & := \frac{(7 + (2 \times (6 + 3)))}{(((10 \times 8) - (9 - 4)) \times 5)} \\
 & := \frac{(7 + (2^{6-3}))}{((1 - (0 - (8 + (9 \times 4)))) \times 5)} & := \frac{(7 + (2 + (6 \times 3)))}{((10^8) \times (9 \times 45))} & := \frac{(7 + (2 + (6 + 3)))}{((10 + (8 + (9 \times 4))) \times 5)} \\
 & := \frac{(7 + (2 + (6 - 3)))}{((10^8) \times (9 \times (4 \times 5)))} & := \frac{(7 + (2 + 63))}{(108 \times (9 - (4 - 5)))} & := \frac{(7 + (26 + 3))}{((10 + (8 + 9)) \times (4 \times 5))} \\
 & := \frac{(7 + (26 - 3))}{(((10^8) + 9) \times 45)} & := \frac{(7 + 263)}{(1 - (0 - 89)) \times 45)} & := \frac{(72 - (6 \times 3))}{((1 - (0 - 89)) \times (4 + 5))} \\
 & := \frac{(72 - (6 - 3))}{(10 - (8 - (9 + (4^5))))} & := \frac{(72 \times (6 \times 3))}{(108 \times (9 \times (4 \times 5)))} & := \frac{(72 \times (6 - 3))}{(1 \times (0 + (8 \times (9 \times 45))))} \\
 & := \frac{(72 + (6^3))}{(10 \times (8 \times (9 + 45)))} & & &
 \end{aligned}$$

3.43 44 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{46328}{57910} & := \frac{(((4 \times 6) + 3) \times 28)}{(5 \times 7) + 910} & := \frac{(((4^{6-3}) + 2) \times 8)}{((57 + 9) \times 10)} & := \frac{(((4 + (6 - 3))^2) \times 8)}{(5 \times (7 + (91 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{((4 - (6 - (3^2))) \times 8)}{((5 - (7 - 9)) \times 10)} & := \frac{((4 \times ((6^3) - 2)) + 8)}{((5 + 7) \times (9 \times 10))} & := \frac{((4 \times (6 \times (3^2))) + 8)}{(5 \times (7 \times (9 - (1 - 0))))} \\
 & := \frac{((4 \times (6 \times (3^2))) - 8)}{(((5 \times 7) - 9) \times 10)} & := \frac{((4 \times (6 \times (3 - 2))) + 8)}{(5 \times (7 - (9 - 10)))} & := \frac{((4 \times (6 + (3^2))) + 8)}{(5 \times (7 + (9 + (1 - 0))))} \\
 & := \frac{((4 \times (63 - 2)) + 8)}{(5 \times (7 \times (9 \times (1 - 0))))} & := \frac{((4 \times 63) + 28)}{(5 \times (7 \times (9 + (1 - 0))))} & := \frac{((4^6 \times (3 - 2)) + 8)}{(57 \times (9 \times 10))} \\
 & := \frac{((4^{6-3}) \times (2 + 8))}{(5 \times ((7 + 9) \times 10))} & := \frac{((4 + ((6 - 3)^2)) \times 8)}{(5 \times (7 + (9 + 10)))} & := \frac{((4 + (6 - (3 - 2))) \times 8)}{((5 \times (7 + 9)) + 10)} \\
 & := \frac{((4 + (6 \times (3 \times 2))) \times 8)}{(5 \times (79 + (1 - 0)))} & := \frac{((4 + (6 \times (3^2))) \times 8)}{(579 + (1 - 0))} & := \frac{(4 - ((6 - 32) \times 8))}{(5 \times ((7 \times 9) - 10))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 - (6 + (3 \times (2 - 8))))}{(5 + (7 + (9 - (1 - 0))))} & := \frac{(4 \times (((6 + 3)^2) + 8))}{(5 \times (79 + 10))} & := \frac{(4 \times ((6 \times (3^2)) + 8))}{(5 \times ((7 \times 9) - (1 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times ((6 + (3 \times 2)) \times 8))}{((57 - 9) \times 10)} & := \frac{(4 \times ((6 + (3 + 2)) \times 8))}{(((5 \times 7) + 9) \times 10)} & := \frac{(4 \times ((6 + (3 - 2))^8))}{(5 \times (7^{9-1+0}))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times (6 - ((3^2) - 8)))}{(5 - ((7 - 9) \times 10))} & := \frac{(4 \times (6 - (3 - (2 + 8))))}{(57 + (9 - (1 - 0)))} & := \frac{(4 \times (6 - (3 \times (2 - 8))))}{((5 + 7) \times (9 + (1 - 0)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 - (3 + (2 - 8))))}{((5 \times 7) + (9 + (1 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times (6 \times (3 + (2 \times 8))))}{(57 \times (9 + (1 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times (6 \times (3 + (2 + 8))))}{(5 \times (79 - (1 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (6^{3^2-8}))}{(5 \times (7 + (9 - 10)))} := \frac{(4 \times (6 + (3 - (2 - 8))))}{(5 \times (7 + (9 - (1 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 \times (6 + (3 + (2 \times 8))))}{((5 \times 7) + (9 \times 10))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (63 - (2 - 8)))}{(5 \times (79 - 10))} := \frac{(4 \times (63 \times (2 + 8)))}{(5 \times (7 \times (9 \times 10)))} := \frac{(4 \times (63 + (2 \times 8)))}{(5 \times (79 \times (1 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4^{6+3 \times 2-8})}{(5 \times ((7 \times 9) + (1 - 0)))} := \frac{(4^{6+3+2-8})}{(5 \times (7 + (9 \times (1 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 + (((6 \times 3) - 2) \times 8))}{(5 + ((7 + 9) \times 10))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + ((6 + 32) \times 8))}{((5 \times 79) - 10)} := \frac{(4 + (6 \times (3 \times (2 \times 8))))}{(5 \times ((7 \times 9) + 10))} := \frac{(4 + (6 \times (3 \times 28)))}{(5 + (7 \times (9 \times 10)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (6 \times (32 + 8)))}{((5 \times (7 \times 9)) - 10)} := \frac{(4 + 6328)}{(5 + 7910)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{48732}{60915}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((4 \times 87) + 32)}{((60 \times (9 - 1)) - 5)} := \frac{((4 + (8 \times (7 - 3))) \times 2)}{(6 \times (0 + (9 + (1 + 5))))} := \frac{((4 + (8 + (7 + 3))) \times 2)}{((6 \times (0 + (9 + 1))) - 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 + (8 + (7 + 3)))^2)}{((60 \times (9 + 1)) + 5)} := \frac{((4 + 8) \times ((7 \times 3) + 2))}{((60 + (9 \times 1)) \times 5)} := \frac{((4 + 8) \times ((7 + 3) \times 2))}{(6 \times (0 + ((9 + 1) \times 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 + 8) \times (7 \times (3 + 2)))}{((60 \times 9) - 15)} := \frac{((48 - (7 - 3)) \times 2)}{(60 + ((9 + 1) \times 5))} := \frac{(4 - (8 - (7 \times 32)))}{(((6 \times (0 + 9)) + 1) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (8 - (7 + (3^2))))}{(6 - (0 - (9 \times (1^5))))} := \frac{(4 - (8 \times (7 - (3^2))))}{((6 + ((0 \times 9) - 1)) \times 5)} := \frac{(4 - (8 \times (7 - 32)))}{((60 - (9 \times 1)) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times ((8 + (7 + 3)) \times 2))}{(60 \times (9 - (1 + 5)))} := \frac{(4 \times ((8 + 7) \times 32))}{(60 \times ((9 - 1) \times 5))} := \frac{(4 \times ((8 + 73) \times 2))}{(6 \times (0 + (9 \times 15)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times ((87 + 3) \times 2))}{(60 \times (9 + (1 + 5)))} := \frac{(4 \times ((87 - 3) \times 2))}{(60 \times (9 + (1 \times 5)))} := \frac{(4 \times (8 - (7 - (3^2))))}{(((6 \times (0 + 9)) + (1 - 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (8 - (7 - (3 - 2))))}{(6 - (0 - (9 - (1 \times 5))))} := \frac{(4 \times (8 \times (7 - (3 - 2))))}{(6 \times (0 + ((9 - 1) \times 5)))} := \frac{(4 \times (8 \times (7 + (3 + 2))))}{(60 \times (9 - (1^5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (8 \times (73 + 2)))}{(60 \times ((9 + 1) \times 5))} := \frac{(4 \times (8 + ((7 + 3)^2)))}{(60 \times (9 \times (1^5)))} := \frac{(4 \times (8 + (7 - (3 \times 2))))}{(60 - (9 + (1 + 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (8 + (7 - (3^2))))}{(6 - (0 - (9 + 15)))} := \frac{(4 \times (8 + (7 - (3 - 2))))}{((6 - (0 - (9 - 1))) \times 5)} := \frac{(4 \times (8 + (7 \times (3 \times 2))))}{(((60 - (9 + 1)) \times 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (8 + (7 \times (3 - 2))))}{((6 - (0 - (9 \times 1))) \times 5)} := \frac{(4 \times (8 + (7 + (3 \times 2))))}{(60 + (9 \times (1 \times 5)))} := \frac{(4 \times (8 + (7 + (3 + 2))))}{(60 + ((9 - 1) \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (8 + (7 + (3 - 2))))}{((6 - (0 - (9 + 1))) \times 5)} := \frac{(4 \times (87 + 32))}{((60 \times (9 + 1)) - 5)} := \frac{(4^{8-7+3-2})}{(6 - (0 - (9 + (1 \times 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4^{8-7 \times (3-2)})}{((6 \times (0 \times 91)) + 5)} := \frac{(4 + (8 \times ((7 \times 3) - 2)))}{(60 + (9 \times 15))} := \frac{(4 + (8 \times (7 - (3 - 2))))}{(((6 \times (0 + (9 + 1))) + 5)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 \times (73 + 2)))}{((60 + 91) \times 5)} := \frac{(4 + (8 + (7 + (3^2))))}{((6 - ((0 \times 9) - 1)) \times 5)} := \frac{(48 \times (7 + (3 \times 2)))}{(60 \times (9 - (1 - 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(48^{7-3 \times 2})}{(6 \times (0 + (9 + (1^5))))} := \frac{(48 + (7 \times 32))}{((60 + (9 - 1)) \times 5)} := \frac{(48 + 732)}{(60 + 915)} \\
 &:= \frac{487 + 3 + 2}{609 + 1 + 5} := \frac{487 + 3 - 2}{609 + 1^5}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.44 46 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{70146}{93528} & := \frac{(((7 + (0 - 1))^4) + 6)}{(((9 + 3)^{5-2}) + 8)} := \frac{(((7 + (0 - 1))^4) - 6)}{(((9 + 3)^{5-2}) - 8)} := \frac{(((70 - 1) \times 4) - 6)}{(9 - 3) \times (52 + 8)} \\
 & := \frac{((7 - (0 - (1 \times 4))) \times 6)}{((9 \times (3 + 5)) + (2 \times 8))} := \frac{((7 - (0 - (1 + 4))) \times 6)}{(((9 + 35) \times 2) + 8)} := \frac{((7 - (0 - (1 + 4)))^6)}{(((9 + 3)^5) \times (2 \times 8))} \\
 & := \frac{((7 - (0 - (1 - 4))) \times 6)}{(((9 + 3) \times 5) - 28)} := \frac{((7 - (0 - 1)) \times (4 \times 6))}{((9 + (3 - (5 \times 2)))^8)} := \frac{((7 - (0 - 14)) \times 6)}{(((93 - 5) \times 2) - 8)} \\
 & := \frac{((7 \times (0 - 1)) + (4 + 6))}{(9 - (3 + ((5 \times 2) - 8)))} := \frac{((7 \times (0 - 1)) + 46)}{(9 + ((3 \times 5) + 28))} := \frac{((7^{-01+4} \times 6))}{((93 + 5) \times 28)} \\
 & := \frac{((7 + (0 - (1^4))) \times 6)}{((9 \times 3) + (5 + (2 \times 8)))} := \frac{((7 + (0 - (1 - 4))) \times 6)}{(((9 + 35) \times 2) - 8)} := \frac{((7 + (0 - 1)) \times (4 \times 6))}{(((9 \times 3) - (5 - 2)) \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{((7 + (0 - 1)) \times 46)}{((9 + (35 + 2)) \times 8)} := \frac{((70 - (1 \times 4)) \times 6)}{((9 + 3) \times (52 - 8))} := \frac{((70 - (1 - 4)) \times 6)}{((9 + ((3 + 5)^2)) \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{((70 + (1 \times 4)) \times 6)}{(((9 \times (3 + 5)) + 2) \times 8)} := \frac{((70 + (1^4)) \times 6)}{((9 \times ((3 + 5)^2)) - 8)} := \frac{((70 + (1 + 4)) \times 6)}{((9 + 3) \times (5 \times (2 + 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{((70 + 14) \times 6)}{((9 + (3 \times (5^2))) \times 8)} := \frac{(7 - (0 - (1 + (4 + 6))))}{(9 - (3 \times (5 - (2 + 8))))} := \frac{(7 - (0 - (1 + (4 - 6))))}{((9 \times (3 - (5 - 2))) + 8)} \\
 & := \frac{(7 - (0 - (1 + 46)))}{(9 \times (3 - (5 - (2 + 8))))} := \frac{(7 - (0 - (14 + 6)))}{(9 \times (3 - (5 + (2 - 8))))} := \frac{(7 - (0 - (14 - 6)))}{(((9 - 3) \times 5) - (2 + 8))} \\
 & := \frac{(7 - (0 - 146))}{(((93 + 5) \times 2) + 8)} := \frac{(7 \times ((0 \times 14) + 6))}{(9 - (3 - (5 \times (2 + 8))))} := \frac{(7 \times (0 + ((1 + 4) \times 6)))}{(9 + ((3^5) + 28))} \\
 & := \frac{(7 \times (0 + (1 - (4 - 6))))}{(9 + ((3^5 - 2) - 8))} := \frac{(7 \times (0 + (1 \times (4 \times 6))))}{(9 + ((3^5) - 28))} := \frac{(7 + (0 - ((1^4) - 6)))}{((9 + (3 - (5 \times 2))) \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{(7 + (0 - (1 - (4 \times 6))))}{((9 + (3 - (5 + 2))) \times 8)} := \frac{(7 + (0 - (1 \times (4 - 6))))}{(9 - (3 \times (5 + (2 - 8))))} := \frac{(70 - ((1^4) - 6))}{((9 \times (3 + 5)) + 28)} \\
 & := \frac{(70 - (1 + (4 \times 6)))}{(9 + (3 \times ((5^2) - 8)))} := \frac{(70 \times ((1^4) \times 6))}{(((9 \times (3 + 5)) - 2) \times 8)} := \frac{(70 + (1 + (4 + 6)))}{(9 + (3 \times (5 + 28)))} \\
 & := \frac{(70 + (1 + (4 - 6)))}{(9 + (3 + (5 \times (2 \times 8))))} := \frac{(70 + (1 + 46))}{((9 - 35) \times (2 - 8))} := \frac{(70 + (14 + 6))}{((9 + (3 + (5 - 2))) \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{(70 + (14 - 6))}{((9 - (3 - (5 + 2))) \times 8)} := \frac{(70 + 146)}{((9 + (3^5 - 2)) \times 8)} := \frac{7014 + 6}{9352 + 8} \\
 & := \frac{7014 - 6}{9352 - 8}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.45 47 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10459}{83672} & := \frac{(((10 + 4) \times 5) - 9)}{(8 \times (((3 + 6) \times 7) - 2))} := \frac{((1 - (0 - (4 + 5))) \times 9)}{(8 \times (3 \times (6 \times (7 - 2))))} := \frac{((1^{04}) - (5 - 9))}{(8 \times (3 - ((6 - 7) \times 2)))} \\
 & := \frac{((1^{04}) \times (5 \times 9))}{(8 \times (3 \times (6 + (7 + 2))))} := \frac{((1^{04}) \times (5 + 9))}{(8 \times (3 + (6 + (7 - 2))))} := \frac{((1^{04}) \times 59)}{((8^3) - ((6 \times 7) - 2))} \\
 & := \frac{((1^{04}) + (5 \times 9))}{(8 \times (3 - (6 - (7^2))))} := \frac{((1^{04}) + 59)}{(8 \times (3 \times (6 + (7 \times 2))))} := \frac{((1 + (0 - (4 - 5)))^9)}{(8^{3+6-7+2})} \\
 & := \frac{((10 - (4 - 5)) \times 9)}{((8 - (3 - 6)) \times 72)} := \frac{((10 \times 4) + (5 \times 9))}{(8 \times (36 + (7^2)))} := \frac{((10 \times 45) - 9)}{(8 \times ((3 + 6) \times (7^2)))} \\
 & := \frac{((10 + (4 \times 5)) \times 9)}{((8 - 3) \times (6 \times 72))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - ((4 + 5) \times 9)))}{(8 + ((3 + 6) \times 72))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (4 - (5 - 9))))}{(8 \times ((3 \times 6) - (7 + 2)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (4 \times (5 + 9))))}{(8 \times (3 + (6 \times (7 + 2))))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (4 + (5 \times 9))))}{(8 \times (36 + (7 \times 2)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (4 + (5 + 9))))}{(83 + (67 + 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (4 + 59)))}{(8^{3^{6-7+2}})} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (45 - 9)))}{(8 \times ((3 \times (6 + 7)) - 2))} := \frac{(1 - (0 \times (4 - 59)))}{(8 - (3 + (6 - (7 + 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - 459))}{(8 + 3672)} := \frac{(1 \times ((0 \times 4) - (5 - 9)))}{(8 \times (3 + (6 - (7 - 2))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 - (4 - (5 \times 9))))}{(8 \times ((3 \times (6 + 7)) + 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 - (4 - (5 + 9))))}{(8 + (3 + (67 + 2)))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 - (4 \times (5 - 9))))}{(8 \times ((3 - (6 - 7))^2))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 - (4 - 59)))}{((8 + 3) \times ((6 \times 7) - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((4 \times 5) + 9)))}{(8 \times (3 + ((6 + 7) \times 2)))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((4 + 5) \times 9)))}{(8 \times (3 + (6 + 72)))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((4 + 5)^9))}{(8 \times ((3 + 6)^{7+2}))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (4 - (5 - 9))))}{(8^{3-6+7-2})} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (4 \times (5 \times 9))))}{(8 \times (36 \times (7 - 2)))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (4 + (5 + 9))))}{(8 \times (3 + (6 + (7 + 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (4 + 59)))}{((8^3) + (6 - (7 \times 2)))} := \frac{(1 + ((0 - (4 - 5))^9))}{(8 \times (3 - (6 - (7 - 2))))} := \frac{(1 + (0 - (4 - (5 + 9))))}{(8 \times (3 - (6 - (7 \times 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (4 \times (5 - 9))))}{(8 - ((3 - 67) \times 2))} := \frac{(10 - (4 \times (5 - 9)))}{(((8 - 3) \times (6 \times 7)) - 2)} := \frac{(10 - (4 - 59))}{((8 + (36 \times 7)) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 + ((4 \times 5) - 9))}{((83 - (6 - 7)) \times 2)} := \frac{(10 + ((4 + 5) \times 9))}{(8 + ((3^6) - (7 + 2)))} := \frac{(10 + (4 + (5 + 9)))}{(8 - ((3 - 6) \times 72))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 + (45 \times 9))}{(83 \times ((6 \times 7) - 2))} := \frac{(104 - (5 - 9))}{(8 \times (36 + 72))} := \frac{(104 + (5 + 9))}{((8^3) + (6 \times 72))} \\
 &:= \frac{(104 + 59)}{(8 + (3 \times (6 \times 72)))} := \frac{(1045 - 9)}{((8^3) + (6^{7-2}))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► **10794**
86352

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((10 - 7) \times 9) + 4)}{((86 \times 3) - (5 \times 2))} := \frac{(((10 - 7) \times 9) - 4)}{(8 \times (6 + ((3 \times 5) + 2)))} := \frac{(((1 - (0 - (7 \times 9)))^4)}{(8^{(6-3) \times (5-2)})} \\
 &:= \frac{(((1 - (0 - 7))^9 - 4)}{(8^{6-3+5-2})} := \frac{((10^7) + (9 + 4))}{((8 + (6 \times (3 + 5))) \times 2)} := \frac{(((1 + (0 - (7 - 9)))^4)}{(8 \times (6 + (3 \times (5^2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((10 \times (7 + 9)) + 4)}{(8 \times ((6^3) - 52))} := \frac{(((10 \times (7 + 9)) - 4)}{(8 \times ((6 - 3) \times 52))} := \frac{(((10 \times 7) - (9 \times 4))}{(8 \times (6 + (3 + (5^2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((10 + (7 - 9)) \times 4)}{((8 + (6 - (3 - 5)))^2)} := \frac{(((10 - 7) \times (9 - 4))}{(8 \times (6 + (3 \times (5 - 2))))} := \frac{(((107 - 9) \times 4)}{((8 + (6 \times (3 + 5)))^2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((1 - ((0 \times 79) - 4))}{((8 - (6 \times (3 - 5))) \times 2)} := \frac{(1 - (0 - ((7 \times 9) - 4)))}{(8 \times (6 \times (3 + (5 + 2))))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (7 - (9 - 4))))}{(1 - (0 - (7 - (9 - 4))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((1 - (0 - (7 \times (9 + 4))))}{(8 \times ((6 \times (3 \times 5)) + 2))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (7 \times (9 - 4))))}{(8 \times (6 \times (3 + (5 - 2))))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (7 + (9 + 4))))}{(8 \times ((6 - 3) \times (5 + 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((1 - (0 - (7 + (9 - 4))))}{(8 \times (6 - (3 - (5 \times 2))))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (7 + 94)))}{(8 \times (6 \times ((3 \times 5) + 2)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (79 \times 4)))}{(8 \times ((63 \times 5) + 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (79 + 4)))}{((8 + (6^3)) \times (5 - 2))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (79 - 4)))}{(8 \times (6 + (35 \times 2)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 \times (7 - 94)))}{(8 - (6 \times (3 - (5 - 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - 794))}{(8 + 6352)} := \frac{(1 \times ((0 - (7 - 9))^4))}{(8 \times (6 + (3 + (5 + 2))))} := \frac{(1 \times ((0 \times 79) + 4))}{(8 - (6 \times (3 - (5 + 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 - ((7 - 9) \times 4)))}{(8^{6+3-5-2})} := \frac{(1 \times (0 - (7 - (9 + 4))))}{(8 \times (6 - (3 - (5 - 2))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((7 + 9) \times 4))}{(8 \times ((6 - (3 - 5))^2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (7 - (9 - 4))))}{(8 \times (6 + (3 - (5 + 2))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (7 + (9 \times 4))))}{(8 \times (6 + (35 + 2)))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (7 + (9 - 4))))}{(8 \times (6 + (3 + (5 - 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (79 - 4)))}{(8 \times ((6 - 3) \times (5^2)))} := \frac{(1 + ((0 - (7 - 9))^4))}{(8 \times (((6 - 3) \times 5) + 2))} := \frac{(1 + (0 - ((7 - 9) \times 4))}{(8 - (6 - (35 \times 2)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (7 - (9 \times 4))))}{(8 \times ((6 - 3) \times (5 \times 2)))} := \frac{(1 + (0 - (7 - (9 + 4))))}{(86 - (3 \times (5 \times 2)))} := \frac{(1 + (0 - (7 - 94)))}{(8 \times ((6 \times (3 \times 5)) - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 - ((7 - 9) \times 4))}{((8 + (6 + (3 - 5)))^2)} := \frac{(10 - (7 - (9 \times 4)))}{(8 \times (6 + (35 - 2)))} := \frac{(10 \times ((7 + 9) \times 4))}{((8^{6-3}) \times (5 \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 \times (7 + (9 + 4)))}{(((8 - 6)^3) \times 5^2)} := \frac{(10 + (7 + (9 \times 4)))}{(8 \times (63 - (5 \times 2)))} := \frac{(10 + (7 + (9 - 4)))}{(8 + (6 \times (3 + (5^2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 + (7 + 94))}{(863 + (5^2))} := \frac{(107 + (9 - 4))}{((8 + 6) \times ((3 + 5)^2))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{17694}{53082}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((1 + (7 - 6)) \times 9) + 4)}{(5 - (3 + (0 - (8^2))))} := \frac{(((1 + 7) \times 6) + 94)}{((53 \times (0 + 8)) + 2)} := \frac{((1^{769}) \times 4)}{(5 - (3 + (0 - (8 + 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1^7) \times ((6 + 9) \times 4))}{(5 \times (30 + (8 - 2)))} := \frac{((1^7) \times (6 + (9 \times 4)))}{(5 + ((3 - (0 - 8))^2))} := \frac{((1 + (7 + 6)) \times (9 + 4))}{(530 + (8 \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (7 + 6)) \times (9 - 4))}{((5 + 30) \times (8 - 2))} := \frac{((1 + (7 - 6)) \times (9 - 4))}{(5 \times (3 \times ((0 \times 8) + 2)))} := \frac{((1 + 7) \times (6 + 94))}{(5 \times (30 \times (8 \times 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 - 7) \times (6 - (9 \times 4)))}{(530 + (8 + 2))} := \frac{(1 - ((7 - (6 + 9)) \times 4))}{(5 + (30 + (8^2)))} := \frac{(1 - (7 - ((6 \times 9) + 4)))}{((5 \times 30) + (8 - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (7 - (6 \times (9 - 4))))}{(5 + (3 - (0 - (8^2))))} := \frac{(1 - (7 - (6 + (9 \times 4))))}{((5 \times (30 - 8)) - 2)} := \frac{(1 - (7 - (6 + (9 + 4))))}{(5 - (30 - (8^2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (7 - (6 + (9 - 4))))}{(5 \times (3 - (0 \times 82)))} := \frac{(1 - (7 - (6 + 94)))}{(((5 + 30) \times 8) + 2)} := \frac{(1 - (7 \times (6 - (9 + 4))))}{(5 \times (3 \times (0 + (8 + 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (((7 \times 6) + 9) \times 4))}{(530 + 82)} := \frac{(1 \times ((7 - (6 - 9)) \times 4))}{(5 \times (30 - (8 - 2)))} := \frac{(1 \times ((7 \times 6) + (9 - 4)))}{((5^3 + 0) + (8 \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((7 + (6 - 9)) \times 4))}{((5 + (3 - 0)) \times (8 - 2))} := \frac{(1 \times (7 - (6 - (9 - 4))))}{(5 + (3 - (0 - (8 + 2))))} := \frac{(1 \times (7^{6-9+4}))}{((5 \times (3 - 0)) + (8 - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (7 + (6 + (9 - 4))))}{((5 + (30 - 8)) \times 2)} := \frac{(1 \times (7 + (69 + 4)))}{(5 \times (3 \times (0 + (8 \times 2))))} := \frac{(1 \times (76 - (9 + 4)))}{((5^3 + 0) + (8^2))} \\
 &:= \frac{1^{7694}}{(5 + ((3 \times (0 \times 8)) - 2))} := \frac{(1 + ((7 - (6 - 9)) \times 4))}{((5^{3+0 \times 8}) - 2)} := \frac{(1 + ((7 \times 6) - (9 + 4)))}{(5 + (3 - (0 - 82)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + ((7 \times 6) + (9 - 4)))}{((5 \times 30) - (8 - 2))} := \frac{(1 + ((7 + (6 - 9)) \times 4))}{(5 + (30 + (8 \times 2)))} := \frac{(1 + ((7 - 6)^{9-4}))}{(5 + (3 + ((0 \times 8) - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (7 - (6 - (9 + 4))))}{(5 \times (3 - (0 - (8 - 2))))} := \frac{(1 + (7 \times (6 + (9 - 4))))}{(((5^3 + 0) - 8) \times 2)} := \frac{(1 + (7^{6-9+4}))}{(5 + (3 - (0 - (8 \times 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (7 + (6 - (9 - 4))))}{(5 + ((3 - (0 - 8)) \times 2))} := \frac{(1 + (7 + (6 \times (9 + 4))))}{(((5 - (3 - 0))^8) + 2)} := \frac{(1 + (7 + (6 + (9 + 4))))}{(5 + ((30 + 8) \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (7 + (6 + (9 - 4))))}{((5 \times (3 - (0 - 8))) + 2)} := \frac{(1 + (7 + (69 + 4)))}{(1 + (7 + (69 + 4)))} := \frac{(1 + (76 - (9 + 4)))}{(1 + (76 - (9 + 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(17 - (6 - 94))}{(5 + (308 + 2))} := \frac{(17 \times (6 \times (9 - 4)))}{(5 \times (308 - 2))} := \frac{(17 + ((6 \times 9) + 4))}{((5 \times (30 + 8)) + 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(17 + (6 + (9 - 4)))}{(5 - (3 + (0 - 82)))} := \frac{(176 - (9 + 4))}{(5 + ((30 - 8)^2))} := \frac{(17 + ((6 \times 9) + 4))}{((5 \times (3 - (0 \times 8)))^2)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{42968}{53710}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((4^2) + 9) \times 68)}{((5^3) \times (7 + 10))} := \frac{(((4^2) - 9) \times (6 \times 8))}{((5 + 37) \times 10)} := \frac{(((4 - 2)^{9-6})^8)}{(((5 + 3)^7) \times 10)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((4 - 2)^9) + 68)}{((5 \times 3) + 710)} := \frac{(((4 - (2 - (9 \times 6))) \times 8))}{((5 + 3) \times (7 \times 10))} := \frac{((4 \times (2 \times (9 + 6))) - 8)}{((5 - 3) \times (7 \times 10))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times (2 \times (9 - 6))) + 8)}{((5 \times (3 + 7)) - 10)} := \frac{((4 \times (2 + (9 + 6))) + 8)}{((5 \times (3 \times 7)) - 10)} := \frac{((4 \times (2 + 9)) + (6 \times 8))}{((5 \times (3 \times 7)) + 10)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (2 + 96)) + 8}{(5 \times ((3 + 7) \times 10))} &:= \frac{((4 \times (29 + 6)) + 8)}{(5 \times (37 \times (1 - 0)))} &:= \frac{((4 \times (29 - 6)) - 8)}{(5 \times (3 \times (7 \times (1 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4^2) \times (9 - (6 - 8)))}{(((5 \times 3) + 7) \times 10)} &:= \frac{((4 + (2 \times 9)) \times (6 \times 8))}{(((5^3) + 7) \times 10)} &:= \frac{((4 + (2^{9-6})) \times 8)}{(5 \times (3 \times (7 + (1 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 + (2 + (9 \times 6))) \times 8)}{((53 + 7) \times 10)} &:= \frac{((4 + (2 + (9 - 6))) \times 8)}{(5 \times (3 \times (7 - (1 - 0))))} &:= \frac{((4 + 2) \times ((9 - 6) \times 8))}{(5 \times (37 - (1 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 - 2) \times (96 + 8))}{((5 + (3 \times 7)) \times 10)} &:= \frac{(4 - ((2 - (9 + 6)) \times 8))}{(5 \times (37 - 10))} &:= \frac{(4 - ((2 - (9 - 6)) \times 8))}{(5 + (3 + (7 \times (1 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - ((2^{9-6}) - 8))}{(5 - (3 + (7 - 10)))} &:= \frac{(4 - (2 - ((9 \times 6) - 8)))}{((5 \times (3 + 7)) + 10)} &:= \frac{(4 - (2 \times (9 \times (6 - 8))))}{(5 \times (3 + (7 \times (1 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (2 + (9 \times (6 - 8))))}{(5 + (3 + (7 + 10)))} &:= \frac{(4 \times (((2 + 9) \times 6) + 8))}{(5 \times (3 + (71 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(4 \times ((2 \times (9 + 6)) + 8))}{(5 \times (37 + (1 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times ((2 \times 96) + 8))}{((5^3) \times (7 + (1 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(4 \times ((2^{9-6}) + 8))}{(((5 \times 3) - 7) \times 10)} &:= \frac{(4 \times ((2 + (9 - 6))^8))}{(5^{3+7-1+0})} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (2 - (9 \times (6 - 8))))}{(5 \times (3 + (7 + 10)))} &:= \frac{(4 \times (2 \times ((9 \times 6) - 8)))}{((53 - 7) \times 10)} &:= \frac{(4 \times (2 \times (9 - (6 - 8))))}{(5 \times ((3 \times 7) + (1 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (2 \times (9 + (6 - 8))))}{(53 + (7 + 10))} &:= \frac{(4 \times (2 + (9 + (6 - 8))))}{(5 \times (3 + (7 - (1 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(4 \times (29 - (6 - 8)))}{(5 \times ((3 \times 7) + 10))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (29 + (6 + 8)))}{(5 + (3 \times (7 \times 10)))} &:= \frac{(4 + ((2 \times (9 \times 6)) + 8))}{((5 + (3 + 7)) \times 10)} &:= \frac{(4 + ((2 \times 9) - (6 + 8)))}{(5 - (3 - (7 + (1 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + ((2 \times 96) + 8))}{(5 \times (3 \times (7 + 10)))} &:= \frac{(4 + ((2 \times 96) - 8))}{(5 \times (37 + 10))} &:= \frac{(4 + ((2^{9-6}) \times 8))}{((5 \times 3) + (7 \times 10))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + ((2 + (9 + 6)) \times 8))}{((5 \times 37) - 10)} &:= \frac{(4 + ((2 + (9 - 6)) \times 8))}{(5 \times (3 + (7 + (1 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(4 + (2 - (9 \times (6 - 8))))}{(5 \times (3 - (7 - 10)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (296 - 8))}{(5 \times (3 + (7 \times 10)))} &:= \frac{(4 + 2968)}{(5 + 3710)}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.46 48 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10679}{85432} &:= \frac{(((1^{06}) + 7) \times 9)}{(8 \times ((5 - 4) \times 3)^2)} &:= \frac{(((1^{06}) + 7)^9)}{(8^5 \times (4 - 3)^2)} &:= \frac{(((10 - 6) \times 7) + 9)}{(8 \times ((5 \times (4 + 3)) + 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((10 - 6)^7) \times 9)}{(8^5 \times (4 + 32))} &:= \frac{((1 - (0 - 6)) \times (7 + 9))}{((8 + (5 \times 4)) \times 32)} &:= \frac{((1^{06}) - (7 - 9))}{(8 \times (5 + (4 - (3 \times 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1^{06}) \times (7 \times 9))}{(8 \times (54 + (3^2)))} &:= \frac{((1^{06}) \times (7 + 9))}{(8 + (5 \times (4 \times (3 \times 2))))} &:= \frac{((1^{06}) \times 79)}{(8 + ((5^4) - (3 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1^{06}) + (7 \times 9))}{(8^{5+4-3 \times 2})} &:= \frac{((1^{06}) + (7 + 9))}{((8 + (5 \times (4 \times 3))) \times 2)} &:= \frac{((1 + (0 - (6 - 7))) \times 9)}{(8 \times (5 + (4 + (3^2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((1 + (0 - (6 - 7))))^9)}{8^{5+4-3-2}} &:= \frac{((10 \times 6) - (7 - 9))}{(8 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3)) + 2))} &:= \frac{((10 + (6 - 7)) \times 9)}{(8 + (5 \times (4 \times 32)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((10 + (6 - 7))^9)}{(8 \times ((5 + 4)^{3^2}))} &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - ((6 \times 7) + 9)))}{(8 \times ((5 \times 4) + 32))} &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - ((6 \times 7) - 9)))}{(8 \times ((5 + (4 \times 3)) \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (6 - (7 - 9))))}{(8 \times (5 + (4 \times (3 - 2))))} &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (6 + (7 \times 9))))}{(8 \times (5 \times ((4 + 3) \times 2)))} &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (6 + (7 + 9))))}{((8 + 54) \times 3) - 2} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (6 + (7 - 9))))}{8 \times (5 \times (4 - 3)^2)} &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (6 + 79)))}{(8 \times (54 + 32))} &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (67 - 9)))}{(8 \times (54 + (3 + 2)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 \times (6 - 79)))}{(8 - (5 + (4 - (3^2))))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - 679))}{(8 + 5432)} := \frac{(1 \times (0 - (6 - (7 + 9))))}{(8 \times (5 - (4 - (3^2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 - (6 \times (7 - 9))))}{(8 \times ((5 + (4 - 3)) \times 2))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((6 \times 7) - 9)))}{(8 \times (5 - (4 - 32)))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (6 - (7 - 9))))}{8^{5-4+3-2}} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (6 \times (7 + 9))))}{(8 \times ((5 + 43) \times 2))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (6 + (7 + 9))))}{(8 \times (54 - 32))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (6 + (7 - 9))))}{(8 \times (5 + (4 - (3 + 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + ((0 - (6 - 7))^9))}{(8 - (5 - (4 + (3^2))))} := \frac{(1 + (0 - (6 - (7 \times 9))))}{(8 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3)) - 2))} := \frac{(1 + (0 - (6 - (7 + 9))))}{(8 \times ((5 \times 4) - (3^2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (6 \times (7 - 9))))}{(8 + ((5 + 43) \times 2))} := \frac{(10 - ((6 - 7) \times 9))}{(8 \times (5 + ((4 + 3) \times 2)))} := \frac{(10 - (6 - (7 \times 9)))}{(10 - (6 - (7 \times 9)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 - (6 - (7 + 9)))}{(10 - (6 - (7 + 9)))} := \frac{(8 \times (5 + ((4^3) - 2)))}{(10 \times ((6 \times 7) - 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 \times (5 \times (4 \times (3 - 2))))}{(10 + (6 \times (7 + 9)))} := \frac{(8 \times (5 - (4 - (3 + 2))))}{(10 + (6 + (7 + 9)))} := \frac{(8 \times (5 \times ((4^3) + 2)))}{(10 + (6 + (7 - 9)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(854 - (3 \times 2))}{(10 + (67 - 9))} := \frac{(8 \times ((5 - 4) \times 32))}{(106 - 79)} := \frac{(8 \times (5 + (4 + (3 + 2))))}{(1067 - 9)} \\
 &:= \frac{((8 + (5 + 4)) \times 32)}{((8 \times 5) - 4) \times (3 \times 2)} := \frac{(85 + (4 + 3))^2}{((85 + (4 + 3))^2)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{10932}{87456}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((1 + 09) \times 3) - 2)}{((8 - 7) \times (4 \times 56))} := \frac{(((10 + 9) \times 3) + 2)}{(8 \times (7 - (4 - 56)))} := \frac{((1 - (0 - (9 - 3)))^2)}{(8 \times (((7 + 4) \times 5) - 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + 09) \times (3^2))}{(8 \times ((7 - 4) \times (5 \times 6)))} := \frac{((1 + 09)^{3 \times 2})}{((8^{7-4}) \times (5^6))} := \frac{((1^{09}) + (3 \times 2))}{(8 + ((7 - (4 - 5)) \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1^{09}) + (3 + 2))}{(87 - (45 - 6))} := \frac{((1^{09}) + 32)}{(8 \times (7 - (4 - (5 \times 6))))} := \frac{((10 \times (9 - 3)) - 2)}{(8 \times (7 + (45 + 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((10 \times 9) - (3 \times 2))}{(8 \times ((7 \times 4) + 56))} := \frac{((10 \times 9) - (3 + 2))}{(8 \times (74 + (5 + 6)))} := \frac{((10 \times 9) + (3^2))}{((87 + 45) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{((10 + (9 + 3)) \times 2)}{(8 \times (74 - (5 \times 6)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - ((9 - 3) \times 2)))}{(8 \times (7 - ((4 - 5) \times 6)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 - (3 + 2))))}{(8 - (7 - (45 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 \times (3 + 2))))}{(8 \times (7 + (45 - 6)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 \times (3 - 2))))}{(8 \times (7 + (4 + (5 - 6))))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 + (3 + 2))))}{((8 - 7) \times (4 \times (5 \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 \times (7 + (45 - 6)))}{(1 - (0 - (9 + (3 - 2))))} := \frac{(8 \times (7 + (4 + (5 - 6))))}{(1 - (0 - (93 + 2)))} := \frac{(8 - 7) \times (4 \times (5 \times 6))}{(1 - (0 \times (9 - 32)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 \times (7 - (4 \times (5 - 6))))}{(1 - (0 - 932))} := \frac{(8 \times ((7 + (4 + 5)) \times 6))}{(1 \times ((0 \times 93) + 2))} := \frac{(8 - (7 + (4 - (5 + 6))))}{(1 \times (0 + ((9 \times 3) + 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 + 7456)}{(8 \times (7 - (4 - (5 - 6))))} := \frac{(8 \times (7 - (4 - (5 - 6))))}{(8 \times (7 - (4 - (5 - 6))))} := \frac{(8 \times ((7 \times 4) - (5 - 6)))}{(8 \times ((7 \times 4) - (5 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((9^3) \times 2)))}{(8 \times (((7 - 4)^5) \times 6))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((9 - 3) \times 2)))}{(8 \times (7 + (4 - (5 - 6))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((9 - 3)^2))}{(8 \times ((7 + (4 - 5)) \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 - (3 \times 2))))}{(8 \times (7 + (4 \times (5 - 6))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 - (3 + 2))))}{(8 \times (7 - (4 + (5 - 6))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 - (3 - 2))))}{8^{7-4+5-6}} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 \times (3^2))))}{((8 \times 74) + 56)} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 \times (3 + 2))))}{((8 + (7 + 45)) \times 6)} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9^3)))}{(8 \times ((7 + (4 \times 5))^6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 \times (3 - 2))))}{(8 \times (((7 - 4) \times 5) - 6))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 + (3^2))))}{((8 + (7 + (4 + 5))) \times 6)} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 + (3 + 2))))}{(8 \times (7 - (4 - (5 + 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 + 32)))}{(8 \times (7 + (4 + (5 \times 6))))} := \frac{(10 \times (9 - (3 + 2)))}{(8 + ((7 + 45) \times 6))} := \frac{(10 \times (9 \times (3^2)))}{(((8 \times 7) + (4^5)) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 + ((9 \times 3)^2))}{(8 \times (745 - 6))} := \frac{(10 + ((9 \times 3) + 2))}{(8 \times ((7 \times 4) + (5 + 6)))} := \frac{(10 + ((9 \times 3) - 2))}{(8 \times (7 \times (4 - (5 - 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 + ((9 - 3) \times 2))}{(8 \times (7 + (4 + (5 + 6))))} := \frac{(10 + (9 \times (3 \times 2)))}{8^{7+4 \times (5-6)}} := \frac{(10 + (9 + 32))}{(8 \times (7 + (4 \times (5 + 6))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(10 + (93 + 2))}{(8 \times (7 \times (4 + (5 + 6))))} := \frac{(109 - (3 + 2))}{(8 \times (74 + (5 \times 6)))} := \frac{(109 - 32)}{((8 + (7 - 4)) \times 56)} \\
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14685}{29370} & := \frac{(((1 - (4 - 6)) \times 8) - 5)}{(2 - (9 \times (3 - (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(((1 - (4 - (6 + 8))) \times 5)}{((2 + 9) \times (3 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{((1^{468}) \times 5)}{(2 \times (9 + (3 - (7 - 0))))} \\
 & := \frac{((1^4) \times (6 \times (8 - 5)))}{(2 + ((9 \times 3) + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{((1^4) \times (6 + (8 \times 5)))}{(2 + (9 \times (3 + (7 - 0))))} := \frac{((1^4) + (6 + (8 + 5)))}{(2 \times ((9 \times 3) - (7 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{((1 + (4 + 6)) \times (8 + 5))}{(293 - (7 - 0))} := \frac{((14 \times 6) - (8 + 5))}{((2^9) - 370)} := \frac{((14 \times 6) + (8 + 5))}{(2 \times ((9 \times 3) + 70))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (4 - ((6 \times 8) - 5)))}{((29 \times 3) - (7 - 0))} := \frac{(1 - (4 - (6 \times (8 - 5))))}{(2 - (9 - (37 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 - (4 - (6 + (8 \times 5))))}{(2 + ((9 + 3) \times (7 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (4 - (6 + (8 + 5))))}{(2^{9+3-7+0})} := \frac{(1 - (4 \times ((6 - 8) \times 5)))}{((2 \times (9 - 3)) + 70)} := \frac{(1 - (4 + (6 - (8 + 5))))}{(29 - (3 \times (7 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (4 + (6 - 85)))}{(2 \times (9 - (3 - 70)))} := \frac{(1 \times (((4 \times 6) - 8)^5))}{((2 + (9 - 3))^7 + 0)} := \frac{(1 \times ((4 - (6 - 8)) \times 5))}{(2 - (9 + (3 - 70)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times ((4 + (6 + 8)) \times 5))}{(2 \times (9 \times (3 + (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 \times (4 - (6 - (8 + 5))))}{(2 + ((9 \times 3) - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 \times (4 \times ((6 + 8) \times 5)))}{((2 + (9 - 3)) \times 70)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (4 + ((6 \times 8) - 5)))}{(2 \times (9 + 3)) + 70} := \frac{(1 \times (4 + (6 - (8 - 5))))}{(2 - (9 - (3 \times (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 \times (4 + (6 \times (8 + 5))))}{(2 \times (9 + (3 + 70)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (4 + (6 \times (8 - 5))))}{(2 + ((9 - 3) \times (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 \times (4 + (68 - 5)))}{((2^9-3) + 70)} := \frac{(1 \times (46 + (8 \times 5)))}{(2 \times (93 - (7 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (46 + (8 - 5)))}{((2 + (9 + 3)) \times (7 - 0))} := \frac{(1 + ((4 \times (6 + 8)) + 5))}{((2 \times (9 \times 3)) + 70)} := \frac{(1 + ((4 \times 6) + (8 - 5)))}{((2 + (9 - 3)) \times (7 - 0))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + ((4 + (6 \times 8)) \times 5))}{((2^9) + (3 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + ((4 + (6 + 8)) \times 5))}{((29 - 3) \times (7 - 0))} := \frac{(1 + ((4 + (6 - 8))^5))}{(2 - (9 - (3 + 70)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + ((4 + 68) \times 5))}{((2^9) + (3 \times 70))} := \frac{(1 + (4 - (6 - (8 \times 5))))}{(2 + (9 - (3 - 70)))} := \frac{(1 + (4 - (6 - 85)))}{(2 \times ((9 + 3) \times (7 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (4 \times (6 - (8 - 5))))}{(2 \times (9 - (3 - (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 + (4 + ((6 \times 8) + 5)))}{((2 \times 93) - 70)} := \frac{(1 + (4 + ((6 \times 8) - 5)))}{(29 - (3 - 70))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (4 + (6 \times (8 - 5))))}{(2 \times (93 - 70))} := \frac{(1 + (4 + (6 + (8 \times 5))))}{(2 + (93 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + (4 + (6 + (8 + 5))))}{(2 + (9 + (37 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (4 + (6 + (8 - 5))))}{((2 - 9) \times (3 - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + (46 - (8 + 5)))}{(2 \times ((9 \times 3) + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + (46 - (8 - 5)))}{(2 + (93 - (7 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + 4685)}{(2 + 9370)} := \frac{(14 \times (6 - (8 - 5)))}{(2 + (9 + (3 + 70)))} := \frac{(14 + (6 \times (8 \times 5)))}{((2^9) + (3 - (7 - 0)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{18306}{27459} & := \frac{(((1^8) + 30) \times 6)}{(((2 + 7) \times 4) - 5) \times 9} := \frac{(((1 + 8) \times 30) + 6)}{(2 + (7 + (45 \times 9)))} := \frac{(((1 + 8) \times 30) - 6)}{(((2 + 7) \times 45) - 9)} \\
 & = \frac{((1 - (8 + 3)) \times (0 - 6))}{((2 + (7 - (4 - 5))) \times 9)} := \frac{((1 - (8 - 30)) \times 6)}{((2 \times 74) + 59)} := \frac{((1^8) - (3 + (0 - 6)))}{(2 - (7 - ((4 \times 5) - 9)))} \\
 & := \frac{((1^8) \times (30 \times 6))}{(2 \times ((7 - 4) \times (5 \times 9)))} := \frac{((1^8) \times 306)}{(((2 \times (7 \times 4)) - 5) \times 9)} := \frac{((1 + (8 - (3 - 0)))^6)}{(((2 \times (7 - 4))^5) \times 9)} \\
 & := \frac{((1 + (8 \times (3 - 0))) \times 6)}{((2 + (7 - 4)) \times (5 \times 9))} := \frac{((1 + (83 - 0)) \times 6)}{(2 \times (7 \times (45 + 9)))} := \frac{((1 + 8) \times (30 - 6))}{((27 + (4 + 5)) \times 9)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + 8) \times 306}{((2 + 7) \times 459)} := \frac{((18 \times (3 - 0)) - 6)}{((18 + (3 - 0)) \times 6)} := \frac{((18 + (3 - 0)) \times 6)}{((18 + (3 - 0)) \times 6)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - 83) \times (0 - 6)}{(2 + (745 - 9))} := \frac{(1 - (8 - (3 - (0 - 6))))}{(2 - (7 - (4 - (5 - 9))))} := \frac{(1 \times ((8 - (3 - 0)) \times 6))}{(2 + (7 + (45 - 9)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(1 \times ((8 \times 30) + 6))}{(((2 + 7) \times 4) + 5) \times 9} := \frac{(1 \times ((8^3 + 0) \times 6))}{((2^7) \times (45 - 9))} := \frac{(1 \times ((8 + (3 - 0)) \times 6))}{(((2 \times (7 - 4)) + 5) \times 9)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (8 - (3 \times (0 \times 6))))}{(2 \times (((7 - 4) \times 5) - 9))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 - (3 \times (0 - 6))))}{((2 \times ((7 - 4) \times 5)) + 9)} := \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (3 - (0 \times 6))))}{(2 - (7 + (4 - (5 \times 9))))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (3 - (0 - 6))))}{(2 \times ((7 + (4 - 5)) \times 9))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (3 \times (0 + 6))))}{(27 \times (4 - (5 - 9)))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (30 + 6)))}{(27 + (45 \times 9))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (30 - 6)))}{(2 \times ((7 + (4 + 5)) \times 9))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 + (30 + 6)))}{(2 + (((7 + 4) \times 5) + 9))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 + (30 - 6)))}{(2 \times (((7 - 4) \times 5) + 9))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (83 \times (0 + 6)))}{(((2^7) - 45) \times 9)} := \frac{(1 + (8 - (3 + (0 - 6))))}{(2 + (7 - ((4 - 5) \times 9)))} := \frac{(1 + (8 + (3 - (0 - 6))))}{(2 + (7 + (4 + (5 + 9))))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (8 + (3 + (0 - 6))))}{(2 + (7 - (4 + (5 - 9))))} := \frac{(1 + (83 - (0 \times 6)))}{(2 \times (7 + (4 \times (5 + 9))))} := \frac{(1 + (83 - (0 - 6)))}{((2 \times (7 \times (4 + 5))) + 9)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + (83 + (0 - 6)))}{((2 \times (7 \times (4 + 5))) - 9)} := \frac{(18 \times (3 - (0 \times 6)))}{((2 - (7 \times (4 - 5))) \times 9)} := \frac{(18 \times (30 \times 6))}{((2 \times (7 + 4)) + 5) \times 9} \\
 & := \frac{(18 \times (3 \times (0 + 6)))}{(2 \times (7 + (4 \times 59)))} := \frac{(18 \times (3^{06}))}{(((2^7 - 4) - 5)^9)} := \frac{(18 \times (30 \times 6))}{(27 \times (4 \times (5 \times 9)))} \\
 & := \frac{(18 \times (30 + 6))}{(27 \times (45 - 9))} := \frac{(18 \times (30 - 6))}{(2 \times ((7 \times 45) + 9))} := \frac{(18 + (30 \times 6))}{(27 \times ((4 \times 5) - 9))} \\
 & := \frac{(18 + (30 - 6))}{(2 + (7 + (45 + 9)))} := \frac{1830 + 6}{2745 + 9} := \frac{1830 - 6}{2745 - 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.47 49 Equivalent Blocks

► $\frac{10592}{84736}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(((1^{05}) + 9) \times 2)}{(8 \times (4 + (7 + (3 + 6))))} := \frac{(((1^{05}) + 9)^2)}{(8 \times (4 \times (7 + (3 \times 6))))} := \frac{((1 - (0 - (5 + 9))) \times 2)}{((8 - 4) \times ((7 + 3) \times 6))} \\
 & := \frac{((1 - (0 - (5 + 9)))^2)}{((8 + (4 \times 73)) \times 6)} := \frac{((1 - (0 - 5)) \times (9 \times 2))}{(8 \times (4 \times ((7 \times 3) + 6)))} := \frac{((1 - (0 - 5)) \times (9 + 2))}{((84 + (7 - 3)) \times 6)} \\
 & := \frac{((1 - (0 - 5)) \times (9 - 2))}{(84 + (7 \times 36))} := \frac{((1^{05}) \times (9 \times 2))}{((8 + (4 \times (7 - 3))) \times 6)} := \frac{((1^{05}) \times (9^2))}{((8 + (4 \times 7)) \times (3 \times 6))} \\
 & := \frac{((1^{05}) \times (9 + 2))}{(8 \times (47 - 36))} := \frac{((1^{05}) + (9 \times 2))}{(8 \times (4 + ((7 \times 3) - 6)))} := \frac{((1 + (0 - (5 - 9))) \times 2)}{(8 \times ((4 \times (7 - 3)) - 6))} \\
 & := \frac{((1 + (0 - (5 - 9)))^2)}{(8 \times (4 - (7 \times (3 - 6))))} := \frac{((10 \times 5) - (9 \times 2))}{(8 - (4 - (7 \times 36)))} := \frac{((10 \times 5) - (9 + 2))}{((8 + (47 - 3)) \times 6)} \\
 & := \frac{((10 + 5) \times (9 - 2))}{(84 \times (7 - (3 - 6)))} := \frac{((105 - 9) \times 2)}{(((8 - 4)^{7-3}) \times 6)} := \frac{(1 - (0 - ((5 \times 9) + 2)))}{(8 \times ((4 + (7 - 3)) \times 6))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (0 - ((5 \times 9) - 2)))}{(8 \times (47 + (3 - 6)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - ((5 + 9) \times 2)))}{(8 \times (4 + (7 + (3 \times 6))))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - ((5 + 9)^2)))}{(847 + (3^6))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 \times (9 + 2))))}{(8 \times (47 + (3 + 6)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 \times (9 - 2))))}{((8 + (4 \times (7 + 3))) \times 6)} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 + (9 \times 2))))}{((8 + 4) \times (7 + (3 + 6)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 + (9 - 2))))}{(8 + (4 \times ((7 - 3) \times 6)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 + 92)))}{(8 + (47 + (3^6)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 \times (5 - 92)))}{(8 - (4 - (7 + (3 - 6))))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (0 - 592))}{(8 + 4736)} := \frac{(1 \times (0 - ((5 - 9) \times 2)))}{(8 \times (4 + (7 + (3 - 6))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 - (5 - (9 + 2))))}{(8 + (4 \times (7 - (3 - 6))))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (0 - (5 - (9 - 2))))}{(8 + (4 + (7 + (3 - 6))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((5 \times 9) + 2)))}{(8 \times (4 + (7 + 36)))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((5 + 9) \times 2)))}{(8 \times (4 + ((7 - 3) \times 6)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (5 \times (9 \times 2))))}{(8 \times ((4 \times (7 \times 3)) + 6))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (5 + (9 + 2))))}{(8 \times (4 \times (7 + (3 - 6))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (5 + (9 - 2))))}{((8 + (4 + (7 - 3))) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (0 - ((5 - 9) \times 2)))}{(8 + (4 \times (7 + (3 + 6))))} := \frac{(1 + (0 - (5 - (9 \times 2))))}{(8 \times (4 + (7 - (3 - 6))))} := \frac{(1 + (0 - (5 - (9 + 2))))}{(8 + ((4 + (7 - 3)) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (5 - (9 - 2))))}{(8 + (4 \times (7 + (3 - 6))))} := \frac{(10 + ((5 + 9) \times 2))}{(8 \times (47 - (3 + 6)))} := \frac{(10 + (5 \times (9 + 2)))}{(8 \times (47 + (3 \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 + (5 + (9 \times 2)))}{(8 \times (4 - (7 - 36)))} := \frac{(10 + (5 + (9^2)))}{(8 \times (4 \times ((7 - 3) \times 6)))} := \frac{(10 + (5 + (9 - 2)))}{(8 \times ((4 \times (7 - 3)) + 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 + (5 + 92))}{(847 + (3 + 6))} := \frac{(10 + (59 + 2))}{(8 \times (4 + (73 - 6)))} := \frac{(10 + (59 - 2))}{(8 \times (4 + (7 \times (3 + 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(105 + (9^2))}{(8 \times (((4 \times 7) + 3) \times 6))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{10742}{85936}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((1^{07}) + 4^2))}{(8 + ((5 + (9 \times 3)) \times 6))} := \frac{((1 - (0 - (7 - 4))) \times 2)}{(8 + (59 + (3 - 6)))} := \frac{((1 - (0 - 7)) \times (4 + 2))}{((8 + (59 - 3)) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 - (0 - 7)) \times 42)}{(8 \times ((59 - 3) \times 6))} := \frac{((1 - (0 - 7))^{4 \times 2})}{(8^{5 \times 9 - 36})} := \frac{((1 - (0 - 7))^{4 - 2})}{(8 + ((5 + 9) \times 36))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((1^{07}) + (4^2)))}{(8 \times (5 + (9 - (3 - 6))))} := \frac{((10 \times (7 - 4)) + 2)}{(8 \times (5 - (9 - 36)))} := \frac{((10 \times 7) - (4 \times 2))}{(8 \times (59 - (3 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((10 \times 7) - (4^2))}{(8 \times ((5 \times (9 + 3)) - 6))} := \frac{((10 \times 7) - (4 - 2))}{(8 \times (59 + (3 + 6)))} := \frac{((10 + 7) \times (4 + 2))}{(8 \times ((5 + (9 + 3)) \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{((10 + 7)^{4 + 2})}{(8 \times ((5 + (9 + 3))^6))} := \frac{((10 - 7) \times (4 + 2))}{((8 + (5 - 9)) \times 36)} := \frac{((10 - 7) \times 42)}{(8 \times ((5 + 9) \times (3 + 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - ((0 \times 74) - 2))}{(8 - (5 - ((9 \times 3) - 6)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - ((7 \times 4) - 2)))}{((8 - (5 - 9)) \times (3 \times 6))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - ((7 + 4)^2)))}{((8 \times 5) + 936)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - ((7 - 4) \times 2)))}{(8 + (((5 + 9) \times 3) + 6))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (7 - (4 - 2))))}{(8 - (5 - (9 + 36)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (7 \times (4 + 2))))}{(8 + ((59 - 3) \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (7 \times (4 - 2))))}{((8 - ((5 - 9) \times 3)) \times 6)} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (7 + (4^2))))}{(8 \times ((5 \times (9 - 3)) - 6))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (7 + 42)))}{(8 \times (5 + (9 + 36)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (74 + 2)))}{(8 \times (5 + ((9 + 3) \times 6)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 \times (7 - 42)))}{(8 - (5 \times (9 - (3 + 6))))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - 742))}{(8 \times (5 + (9 + (3^6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 - (7 - (4^2))))}{((8 + (5 - 9)) \times (3 \times 6))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((7 \times 4) + 2)))}{(8 \times (5 \times (9 + (3 - 6))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((7 \times 4) - 2)))}{(8 \times (5 + ((9 \times 3) - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (7 - (4 - 2))))}{(8 + (5 - (9 - 36)))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (7 \times (4 \times 2))))}{(8 \times (59 + (3 - 6)))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (7 \times (4 + 2))))}{(8 \times ((5 \times 9) + (3 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (7 \times (4 - 2))))}{(8 \times (5 - (9 - (3 \times 6))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (7 + (4^2))))}{(8 \times (5 + (9 + (3 + 6))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (74 - 2)))}{((8 - (5 - 93)) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (7 - (4^2))))}{(8 - ((5 - 9) \times (3 \times 6)))} := \frac{(1 + (0 - (7 - 42)))}{(8 \times ((5 \times (9 - 3)) + 6))} := \frac{(10 - ((7 - 4) \times 2))}{(8 + ((5 \times (9 - 3)) - 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 - (7 - (4^2)))}{(8 - ((5 - 9) \times 36))} := \frac{(10 \times ((7 - 4) \times 2))}{(8 \times (5 \times (9 - (3 - 6))))} := \frac{(10 \times (7 + (4 - 2)))}{(8 \times (5 \times (9 + (3 + 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 + (7 - (4 + 2)))}{(8 \times (5 + (9 + (3 - 6))))} := \frac{(10 + (7 \times (4 \times 2)))}{(8 \times ((5 + (9 - 3)) \times 6))} := \frac{(10 + (74 + 2))}{(8 \times (5 + (9 \times (3 + 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(107 - (4 \times 2))}{((8 + (5 + 9)) \times 36)} := \frac{(107 - (4 + 2))}{(85 + ((9^3) - 6))} := \frac{(107 - (4 - 2))}{(8 \times (5 \times ((9 \times 3) - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(107 \times (4 + 2))}{(859 - 3) \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10836}{97524} &:= \frac{(((1 - (0 - 8)) \times 3) + 6)}{(9 + ((7 + 5) \times 24))} := \frac{(((1 - (0 - 8)) \times 3) - 6)}{(9 \times (7 \times (5 + (2 - 4))))} := \frac{(((10 + 8) \times 3) + 6)}{(9 + (7 + 524))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((10 - 8)^3) \times 6)}{(9 \times ((7 - 5) \times 24))} := \frac{(((10 - 8)^3) + 6)}{(9 \times (7 + (5 - (2 - 4))))} := \frac{((1 - (0 - (8 + 3)))^6)}{(9 \times ((7 + 5)^{2+4}))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((1 - (0 - (8 - 3))) \times 6)}{(9 \times (7 + (5 + 24)))} := \frac{(((1 - (0 - 8)) \times (3 + 6))}{(9 \times (75 + (2 + 4)))} := \frac{((1^{08}) - (3 - 6))}{(9 \times (7 - (5 + (2 - 4))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1^{08}) \times (3^6))}{9^{7-5-2+4}} := \frac{((1^{08}) \times (3 + 6))}{(9 - ((7 - (5^2)) \times 4))} := \frac{((1^{08}) + 36)}{(9 \times (7 + (5 \times (2 + 4))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((10 \times (8 - 3)) + 6)}{(9 \times ((7 + (5 + 2)) \times 4))} := \frac{((10 \times 8) - (3 - 6))}{(9 \times (75 + (2 \times 4)))} := \frac{((10 \times 8) + (3 \times 6))}{(9 \times (7 \times ((5 \times 2) + 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - ((8 \times 3) - 6)))}{(9 \times (7 + ((5 - 2) \times 4)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - ((8 + 3) \times 6)))}{(9 \times (75 - (2 \times 4)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (8 - (3 - 6))))}{(9 \times (7 \times ((5 \times 2) + 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (8 \times (3 + 6))))}{(9 \times (75 + (2 - 4)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (8 + (3 \times 6))))}{(9 \times ((7 \times 5) - (2 \times 4)))} := \frac{((9 - (7 - (5^2))) \times 4)}{(1 - (0 - (8 + (3 + 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (8 + (3 - 6))))}{(9 \times (7 + (5 - (2 + 4))))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (8 + 36)))}{(9 \times ((7 \times 5) - (2 \times 4)))} := \frac{(9 \times (7 - (5 - (2^4))))}{(1 - (0 \times (8 - 36)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 \times (7 + (5 - (2 + 4))))}{(1 - (0 - 836))} := \frac{(9 \times ((7 \times (5 + 2)) - 4))}{(1 \times ((0 \times 8) - (3 - 6)))} := \frac{(9 - (7 - (5 - (2 - 4))))}{(1 \times (0 - (8 - (3 \times 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 + 7524)}{(1 \times (0 - (8 \times (3 - 6))))} := \frac{(9 + (7 - (5 - (2^4))))}{(1 \times (0 - (8 - 36)))} := \frac{(9 \times (7 + (5 + (2 - 4))))}{(1 \times (0 + ((8 + 3) \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((9 - (7 - 52)) \times 4)}{(1 \times (0 + (8 - (3 - 6))))} := \frac{(9 \times (7 + (5 + (2^4))))}{(1 \times (0 + (8 \times (3 \times 6))))} := \frac{(9 \times ((7 \times (5 \times 2)) - 4))}{(1 \times (0 + (8 \times (3 + 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 \times ((7 \times 5) - 24))}{(1 \times (0 + (8 \times 36)))} := \frac{((9 + (7 - (5 \times 2)))^4)}{(1 \times (0 + (8 + (3 \times 6))))} := \frac{((9^{7-5}) \times (2 \times 4))}{(1 \times (0 + (8 + (3 + 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 \times ((7 + 5) \times 24))}{(1 \times (0 + (8 + (3 - 6))))} := \frac{(9 \times (7 - (5 - 24)))}{(1 \times (0 + (8 + 36)))} := \frac{(9 \times (7 - (5 \times (2 - 4))))}{(1 \times (0 + (83 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 + (7 + (5 + 24)))}{(1 + (0 - (8 - (3 + 6))))} := \frac{(((9 + 7) \times (5^2)) - 4)}{(1 + (0 - (8 \times (3 - 6))))} := \frac{(9 \times (7 \times (5 + (2 + 4))))}{(1 + (0 - (8 - 36)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((9 - (7 - 5)) \times 2) + 4)}{(10 - (8 - (3 \times 6)))} := \frac{(9 \times ((7 \times (5 - 2)) + 4))}{(10 + ((8 - 3) \times 6))} := \frac{(9 \times ((7 \times 5) - (2 + 4)))}{(10 + (8 \times (3 \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 \times (7 + (5 + (2 \times 4))))}{(10 + (8 + 36))} := \frac{(9 \times ((7 + (5 - 2)) \times 4))}{(10 + (83 + 6))} := \frac{(9 \times ((75 \times 2) + 4))}{(10 + (83 - 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{((9^{7-5}) \times (2 + 4))}{(108 - (3 - 6))} := \frac{(9 \times (75 + 24))}{(9 \times (75 + 24))} := \frac{(9 \times (7 + (5 \times (2^4))))}{(9 \times (75 + 24))} \\
 &:= \frac{(108 - (3 - 6))}{(975 + 24)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{38451}{76902} &:= \frac{((3 \times ((8 - 4) \times 5)) + 1)}{((7 + (6 \times (9 - 0))) \times 2)} := \frac{((3 \times (8 \times 4)) + 51)}{(7 \times (6 \times (9 + (0 - 2))))} := \frac{((3 \times (8 + (4 \times 5))) + 1)}{((76 + (9 - 0)) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (8 + (4 - 5))) + 1)}{((7 + (6 + (9 - 0))) \times 2)} := \frac{((3 \times (8 - 4)) - (5 + 1))}{(7 - (6 - (9 - (0 - 2))))} := \frac{((3 \times (8 - 4)) - (5 - 1))}{((7 + (6 - (9 - 0)))^2)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (84 + 5)) - 1)}{(76 \times (9 + (0 - 2)))} := \frac{((3 \times 8) + (4 \times (5 \times 1)))}{((7 - 6) \times (90 - 2))} := \frac{((3 \times 8) + (4 + (5 \times 1)))}{(((7 \times 6) - (9 - 0)) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3^{8-4}) + 51)}{(((7 \times 6) + 90) \times 2)} := \frac{((3 + (8 + 4)) \times (5 + 1))}{((7 - 6) \times (90 \times 2))} := \frac{((3 + 8) \times ((4 \times 5) + 1))}{(7 \times (6 \times (9 - (0 - 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((38 \times (4 + 5)) + 1)}{(7 \times (6 + (90 + 2)))} := \frac{((38 \times (4 + 5)) - 1)}{((76 \times (9 - 0)) - 2)} := \frac{(3 - (8 - (4 + (5 \times 1))))}{(7 - (6 - (9 + (0 - 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (8 - (4 + (5 + 1))))}{(7 - (6 - (9 - (0 \times 2))))} := \frac{(3 - (8 - (4 + 51)))}{((7 - (6 - (9 - 0)))^2)} := \frac{(3 - (8 - (45 + 1)))}{(7 - (6 - (9^{02})))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(3 - (8 - (45 - 1)))}{(7 + (69 - (0 - 2)))} := \frac{(3 - (8 \times (4 - (5 \times 1))))}{(7 + (6 + (9 - (0 \times 2))))} := \frac{(3 - (8 \times (4 - (5 - 1))))}{(7 + (6 - (9 + (0 - 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times ((8 \times (4 \times 5)) + 1))}{(7 \times (69 \times (0 + 2)))} := \frac{(3 \times ((8 \times 4) + (5 \times 1)))}{((7 \times 6) + (90 \times 2))} := \frac{(3 \times (8 - (4 - (5 + 1))))}{((7 \times 6) - (9 \times (0 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (8 + (4 - (5 \times 1))))}{(7 \times (6 - (9 \times (0 \times 2))))} := \frac{(3 \times (8 + (4 \times (5 \times 1))))}{(7 \times (6 - (9 \times (0 - 2))))} := \frac{(3 \times (8 + (4 + (5 \times 1))))}{(((7 \times 6) + (9 - 0)) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (8 + (4 + 51)))}{(7 \times (6 \times (9 - (0 \times 2))))} := \frac{(3 + (((8 + 4) \times 5) - 1))}{(3 + (((8 \times 4) \times 5) - 1))} := \frac{(3 + ((8 \times (4 + 5)) + 1))}{((7 + (69 - 0)) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + ((8 \times 4) - (5 + 1)))}{(76 + (9 \times (0 - 2)))} := \frac{(3 + (8 - (4 - (5 \times 1))))}{(7 + (6 + (9 - (0 - 2))))} := \frac{(3 + (8 - (4 + (5 \times 1))))}{(7 + (6 - (9 - (0 \times 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (8 - (4 + (5 + 1))))}{(7 + (6 - (9 - (0 - 2))))} := \frac{(3 + (8 \times (4 + (5 - 1))))}{(7 + (6 + (9 + (0 - 2))))} := \frac{(3 + (8 + (4 - (5 \times 1))))}{(7 + (6 - (9 - (0 \times 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (8 + (4 - (5 + 1))))}{((7 - 6) \times (9 \times (0 + 2)))} := \frac{(3 + (84 - (5 \times 1)))}{(76 + (90 - 2))} := \frac{(3 + (84 + (5 - 1)))}{((7 - (6 - 90)) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(38 - (4 - (5 - 1)))}{(7 + (69 - (0 \times 2)))} := \frac{(38 \times (4 + (5 \times 1)))}{(76 \times (9 - (0 \times 2)))} := \frac{(38 + (4 - (5 \times 1)))}{(7 + (69 + (0 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(38 + (4 \times 51))}{((7 + (6 + (9 - 0)))^2)} := \frac{(384 - 5 - 1)}{(7 + (6 + (9^{02})))} := \frac{(3845 + 1)}{((7 - 6) \times (90 + 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{38 + 451}{76 + 902} := \frac{384 - 5 - 1}{7 \times 6 \times 9 \times 02} := \frac{3845 + 1}{7690 + 2} \\
 &:= \frac{3845 - 1}{7690 - 2}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.48 50 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10954}{87632} &:= \frac{(((1 + 09) \times 5) + 4)}{((8 - 7) \times ((6^3) \times 2))} := \frac{(((1^{09}) + 5) \times 4)}{((87 + (6 + 3)) \times 2)} := \frac{((1 - (0 - (9 - 5))) \times 4)}{(8 \times ((7 + (6 - 3)) \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 - (0 - (9 - 5)))^4)}{(8 \times ((7 + (6 \times 3))^2))} := \frac{((1 + 09) \times (5 \times 4))}{((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 32)} := \frac{((1 + 09) \times (5 + 4))}{(8 \times (((7 \times 6) + 3) \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 - (0 - 95))^4)}{((8^7) \times ((6 \times 3)^2))} := \frac{((1^{09}) + (5 \times 4))}{((87 - (6 - 3)) \times 2)} := \frac{((1^{09}) + (5 - 4))}{(8 - (7 - (6 + (3^2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((10 \times (9 \times 5)) - 4)}{(8 \times ((7 + (6^3)) \times 2))} := \frac{((10 \times (9 - 5)) + 4)}{(8 \times (76 - 32))} := \frac{((10 \times (9 - 5)) - 4)}{((8 + (7 - 6)) \times 32)} \\
 &:= \frac{((10 \times 9) - (5 \times 4))}{(8 \times (76 - (3 \times 2)))} := \frac{((109 + 5) \times 4)}{(8 \times (76 \times (3 \times 2)))} := \frac{((109 - 5) \times 4)}{(8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 32))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - ((0 \times 95) - 4))}{(8 + ((7 + (6 + 3)) \times 2))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - ((9 \times 5) + 4)))}{(8 \times ((7 + (6 \times 3)) \times 2))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - ((9 \times 5) - 4)))}{(8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (3 - 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - ((9 - 5) \times 4)))}{(8 + ((7 \times (6 \times 3)) + 2))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 \times (5 + 4))))}{(8 \times (76 + (3 \times 2)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 \times (5 - 4))))}{(8 \times (7 - (6 - (3^2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 + (5 \times 4))))}{((8 + 7) \times ((6 \times 3) - 2))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 + (5 + 4))))}{(8 \times (7 + (6 + (3 \times 2))))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 + (5 - 4))))}{(87 + (6 - (3 + 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 + 54)))}{8^{(7-6)^3+2}} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (95 + 4)))}{(8 \times ((7 + (6 - 3))^2))} := \frac{(1 - (0 \times (9 - 54)))}{(8^{7-6 \times (3-2)})} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - 954))}{(8 + 7632)} := \frac{(1 \times ((0 \times 95) + 4))}{(8 \times (7 + (6 - (3^2))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 - (9 - 54)))}{(8 \times (7 + (6 + 32)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((9 \times 5) + 4)))}{(8 \times (7 \times (6 + (3 - 2))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((9 \times 5) - 4)))}{(8 \times (((7 + 6) \times 3) + 2))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((9 - 5) \times 4)))}{((8 - (7 - 63)) \times 2)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((9 - 5)^4)))}{(8 \times ((7 + (6 + 3))^2))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 - (5 - 4))))}{8^{7-6+3-2}} &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 \times (5 + 4))))}{(8 \times (76 + (3 + 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 \times (5 - 4))))}{(8 \times ((7 - 6) \times (3^2)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 + (5 + 4))))}{(8 \times (7 + (6 + (3 + 2))))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 + 54)))}{(8 \times (7 \times ((6 - 3)^2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (95 \times 4)))}{((8 + (7 \times (6^3))) \times 2)} &:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (9 - (5 \times 4))))}{(8 \times (7 + (6 - (3 - 2))))} &:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (9 - 54)))}{((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 32)} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 \times (9 - (5 - 4)))}{((8 \times 76) + 32)} &:= \frac{(10 \times (9 \times (5 + 4)))}{((8 + 7) \times ((6^3) \times 2))} &:= \frac{(10 + ((9 \times 5) + 4))}{((8 + (76 \times 3)) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 + ((9 \times 5) - 4))}{(8 \times ((7 \times 6) + (3^2)))} &:= \frac{(10 + ((9 + 5) \times 4))}{((87 \times 6) + (3 \times 2))} &:= \frac{(10 + ((9 - 5)^4))}{(8 \times (7 \times (6 + 32)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 + (9 + (5 + 4)))}{((8 - (7 - 6)) \times 32)} &:= \frac{(109 - (5 - 4))}{(8 \times (76 + 32))} &
 \end{aligned}$$

3.49 51 Equivalent Blocks

► **30186**
45279

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((3 - (0 - 1)) \times 8) + 6)}{(4 - ((5 \times 2) - (7 \times 9)))} &:= \frac{(((3 - (0 - (1 \times 8))) \times 6)}{(((4 + 5) \times 2) - 7) \times 9} &:= \frac{(((3 - (0 - (1^8))) \times 6)}{(4 \times (5 + (2 - (7 - 9))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((3 - (0 - 1)) \times (8 \times 6))}{(4 + (5 + 279))} &:= \frac{(((3 - (0 - 1)) \times (8 + 6))}{((4 \times (5^2)) - (7 + 9))} &:= \frac{(((3 - (0 - 18)) \times 6)}{((4 \times (5 \times (2 + 7))) + 9)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (0 \times 1)) + (8 + 6))}{((4 \times (5^2)) - 79)} &:= \frac{((3 \times (0 \times 1)) + 86)}{((4 \times 52) - 79)} &:= \frac{((3 \times (0 + (1 \times 8))) + 6)}{(4 + (5 + (27 + 9)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (0 + 18)) + 6)}{(4 + (5 + (2 + 79)))} &:= \frac{((3 \times (0 + 18)) - 6)}{((4 - (5 - (2 + 7))) \times 9)} &:= \frac{((3^{01 \times 8}) \times 6)}{((4 + 5)^{2 \times 7 - 9})} \\
 &:= \frac{(((3 + (0 - (1^8))) \times 6)}{(4 - ((5 + 2) \times (7 - 9)))} &:= \frac{(((3 + (0 - (1^8)))^6)}{((4 - 52) \times (7 - 9))} &:= \frac{(((3 + (0 - 1)) \times (8 \times 6))}{(4 \times ((5 \times (2 + 7)) - 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((3 + (0 - 1)) \times (8 + 6))}{(4 - ((5^2) - (7 \times 9)))} &:= \frac{(((30 - (1 \times 8)) \times 6)}{((4 + ((5^2) - 7)) \times 9)} &:= \frac{(((30 - (1^8)) \times 6)}{((4 - (5 \times (2 - 7))) \times 9)} \\
 &:= \frac{((30 \times (1 + 8)) + 6)}{((45 \times (2 + 7)) + 9)} &:= \frac{((30 \times (1 + 8)) - 6)}{((45 \times (2 + 7)) - 9)} &:= \frac{((30 + (1^8)) \times 6)}{((45 - (2 \times 7)) \times 9)} \\
 &:= \frac{((30 + 1) \times (8 - 6))}{((4 \times ((5 - 2) \times 7)) + 9)} &:= \frac{((30 - 1) \times (8 \times 6))}{((45^2) + (7 \times 9))} &:= \frac{(3 - (0 - ((1^8) + 6)))}{(4 - (52 - (7 \times 9)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (0 - (1^{86})))}{((4 - (5 + 2)) \times (7 - 9))} &:= \frac{(3 - (0 - (1 + (8 + 6))))}{(4 + (5 + (2 + (7 + 9))))} &:= \frac{(3 - (0 - (1 + (8 - 6))))}{(4 + (5 - (2 + (7 - 9))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (0 - (1 + 86)))}{(4 + (5 + (2 \times (7 \times 9))))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (1 \times (8 \times 6))))}{(4 \times ((5 \times (2 + 7)) + 9))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (1 \times (8^6))))}{((4^5) \times ((2^7) \times 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (1 \times (8 + 6))))}{((4 \times ((5^2) - 7)) - 9)} &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (18 \times 6)))}{((45 + (2 + 7)) \times 9)} &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (18 + 6)))}{(4 - (52 \times (7 - 9)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (18 - 6)))}{(4 + (5 - ((2 - 7) \times 9)))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + 186))}{(((4 \times (5^2)) - 7) \times 9)} &:= \frac{(3 + (0 - ((1^8) - 6)))}{((4 \times (5 + 2)) - (7 + 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (0 - (1 - (8 \times 6))))}{((4 \times ((5 - 2) \times 7)) - 9)} &:= \frac{(3 + (0 - (1 - (8 + 6))))}{(4 + (5 \times (2 - (7 - 9))))} &:= \frac{(3 + (0 - (1^{86})))}{(4 - (5 - (2 - (7 - 9))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(30 \times ((1^8) + 6))}{(((4 \times (5 + 2)) + 7) \times 9)} &:= \frac{(30 \times (18 \times 6))}{(4 \times (5 \times (27 \times 9)))} &:= \frac{(30 \times (18 - 6))}{(4 + (527 + 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{(30 + ((1 + 8) \times 6))}{((4 + (5 - (2 - 7))) \times 9)} &:= \frac{(30 + (1 \times (8 \times 6)))}{((4 - (5 - (2 \times 7))) \times 9)} &:= \frac{(30 + (1 \times (8 + 6)))}{((4^{5-2}) - (7 - 9))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(30 + (1 \times (8 - 6)))}{(4 \times (((5 - 2) \times 7) - 9))} := \frac{(30 + (18 \times 6))}{((4 + (5 + (2 \times 7))) \times 9)} := \frac{(30 + (18 + 6))}{((4 \times ((5^2) - 7)) + 9)} \\ &:= \frac{(30 + 186)}{((4 + (5 + 27)) \times 9)} := \frac{(3018 + 6)}{(4527 + 9)} := \frac{(3018 - 6)}{(4527 - 9)} \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{61830}{92745}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(((6 + 1) \times 8) - 30)}{(9 + (2 \times ((7 - 4) \times 5)))} := \frac{(((6 - 1) \times 8) + 30)}{(92 - (7 - (4 \times 5)))} := \frac{(((6 - (1 - 8)) \times 30)}{(9 \times (2 + (7 \times (4 + 5))))} \\ &:= \frac{((6 \times (1 + 8)) + 30)}{((9 - (2 - 7)) \times (4 + 5))} := \frac{((6 \times 18)^3 + 0)}{((9 - (2 - (7 + 4)))^5)} := \frac{((6 \times 18) - 30)}{(9 \times ((2^7 - 4) + 5))} \\ &:= \frac{((6 + (1 \times 8)) \times (3 - 0))}{(9 + (2 + (7 + 45)))} := \frac{((6 + (1 \times 8)) \times 30)}{((9 - (2 - 7)) \times 45)} := \frac{((6 + (1^8)) \times 30)}{(9 \times (2 + ((7 \times 4) + 5)))} \\ &:= \frac{((6 + 1) \times (8 \times (3 - 0)))}{(9 \times (27 - (4 - 5)))} := \frac{((6 + 1) \times (8 \times 30))}{(9 \times (2 \times (7 \times (4 \times 5))))} := \frac{((6 - 1) \times (8 \times (3 - 0)))}{((9 + (2 - 7)) \times 45)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - ((1^8) - (3 - 0)))}{(9 + ((2^7 - 4) - 5))} := \frac{(6 - (1 - (8 - (3 - 0))))}{(9 - (2 - (7 - (4 - 5))))} := \frac{(6 - (1 - (8 + (3 - 0))))}{(9 + (2 - (7 - (4 \times 5))))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - (1 \times (8 - 30)))}{((9 - 2) \times (7 + (4 - 5)))} := \frac{(6 \times ((1^8) \times 30))}{(9 \times (2 \times ((7 - 4) \times 5)))} := \frac{(6 \times ((1^8) + (3 - 0)))}{(9 \times (2 - (7 - (4 + 5))))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times ((1^8) + 30))}{(9 \times (((2 + 7) \times 4) - 5))} := \frac{(6 \times ((1 + 8) \times (3 - 0)))}{((9 - (2 \times (7 - 4)))^5)} := \frac{(6 \times ((1 + 8)^3 + 0))}{(9^{2-7+4+5})} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times (1 - (8 - 30)))}{(9 \times ((2 \times 7) + (4 + 5)))} := \frac{(6 \times (1 \times (8 - (3 - 0))))}{(9 - (2 + (7 - 45)))} := \frac{(6 \times (1 \times (8 + (3 - 0))))}{(9 \times ((2 \times (7 - 4)) + 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times (1 \times (83 - 0)))}{(9 \times ((2^7) - 45))} := \frac{(6 \times (1 + (8 - (3 - 0))))}{(9 - ((2 - (7 + 4)) \times 5))} := \frac{(6 \times (1 + (8 \times (3 - 0))))}{(9 \times ((2 + (7 - 4)) \times 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times (1 + (8 + (3 - 0))))}{(9 \times (2 \times (7 + (4 - 5))))} := \frac{(6 \times (1 + (83 - 0)))}{(9 + (2 + 745))} := \frac{(6 \times (18 \times (3 - 0)))}{(9 \times (2 + (7 + 45)))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times (18 \times 30))}{(9 \times (27 \times (4 \times 5)))} := \frac{(6 \times (18 + (3 - 0)))}{(9 + ((2 + 7) \times (4 \times 5)))} := \frac{6^{1^8 \times 3 + 0}}{9 \times (27 + 4 + 5)} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times (1^{830}))}{(9 - (2 + (7 - (4 + 5))))} := \frac{(6 \times (1 + (8 - (3 - 0))))}{(9 \times ((2 \times (7 - 4))^5))} := \frac{(6 + ((1^8) - (3 - 0)))}{(9 - ((2^7 - 4) - 5))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + ((1 + 8) \times 30))}{(9 \times (2 \times ((7 \times 4) - 5)))} := \frac{(6 + (1 - (8 - (3 - 0))))}{(6 + (1 - (8 - (3 - 0))))} := \frac{(6 + (1 \times (8 \times 30)))}{(6 + (1 \times (8 \times 30)))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + (1 \times (8 + 30)))}{(9 + (2 + ((7 + 4) \times 5)))} := \frac{(6 + (1 + (8 - (3 - 0))))}{(9 + (2 - (7 - (4 - 5))))} := \frac{(9 - ((2 - 74) \times 5))}{(6 + (1 + (8 + (3 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 + (1 + (83 - 0)))}{(9 + (2 + ((7 + 4) \times 5)))} := \frac{(6 + (18 \times (3 - 0)))}{(6 + (18 \times (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(9 + (2 + (7 + (4 + 5))))}{(6 + (18 \times 30))} \\ &:= \frac{(9 + (2 \times (7 \times (4 + 5))))}{(6 + (18 + 30))} := \frac{(9 \times (2 + (7 - (4 - 5))))}{(6 + 1830)} := \frac{(((9 + 2) \times 74) + 5)}{((9 + 2) \times 74) + 5} \\ &:= \frac{(9 \times (2 - (7 \times (4 - 5))))}{(61 - (8 + (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(9 + 2745)}{(618 + 30)} := \frac{(61 - (8 - (3 - 0)))}{(618 - 30)} \\ &:= \frac{(61 - (8 + (3 - 0)))}{((9 + (2 \times (7 - 4))) \times 5)} := \frac{(618 + 30)}{(9 \times ((2^7) - (4 \times 5)))} := \frac{(618 - 30)}{(927 - 45)} \end{aligned}$$

3.50 52 Equivalent Blocks

► $\frac{46185}{92370}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(((4 \times 6) - 1) \times 8) + 5}{(9 \times (2 \times (3 \times (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(((4 \times 6) + (1^8)) \times 5)}{(((9^2) \times 3) + (7 - 0))} := \frac{(((4 + (6 - 1)) \times 8) + 5)}{((9^2) + (3 + 70))} \\ &:= \frac{(((4 + 6) \times 18) - 5)}{(((9 - 2)^3) + (7 - 0))} := \frac{(((4 + 61) \times 8) + 5)}{((9 + (2 \times 3)) \times 70)} := \frac{((4 - (6 - (1 \times 8))) \times 5)}{((9^2) - (3 \times (7 - 0)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((4 - (6 - (1 + 8))) \times 5)}{(9 - (2^3)) \times 70} := \frac{((4 - (6 - 18))^5)}{((9 + (2 - 3))^7 + 0)} := \frac{((4 \times (6 \times 1)) + (8 - 5))}{(9 \times (2 - (3 - (7 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times (6 \times (1^8))) - 5)}{((9 \times (2 + 3)) - (7 - 0))} := \frac{((4 \times 6) - (1 - (8 - 5)))}{((9 \times (2 + 3)) + (7 - 0))} := \frac{((4 \times 6) + (18 \times 5))}{((9 \times 2) + (3 \times 70))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times 61) - (8 + 5))}{(92 + 370)} := \frac{((4 + (6 - (1 - 8))) \times 5)}{(9 + (23 \times (7 - 0)))} := \frac{((4 + (6 + (1 \times 8))) \times 5)}{(9 \times (2 \times (3 + (7 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 + (6 + (1^8))) \times 5)}{((9 + 2) \times (3 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{((4 + (6 + 18)) \times 5)}{((9 - (2 + 3)) \times 70)} := \frac{((4 - 6) \times (1 - 85))}{(((9 - 2)^3) - (7 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{((46 - 1) \times (8 - 5))}{(9 \times (23 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 - ((6 \times (1 - 8)) + 5))}{(92 - (3 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 - (6 - ((1^8) + 5)))}{(9 - ((2^3) - (7 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (6 - (1 \times (8 - 5))))}{((9 \times (2^3)) - 70)} := \frac{(4 - (6 - (1 + (8 \times 5))))}{(9 + (2 - (3 - 70)))} := \frac{(4 - (6 + (1 - (8 \times 5))))}{(9 - (2 + (3 - 70)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times ((6 + (1 \times 8)) \times 5))}{((9 + (2 - 3)) \times 70)} := \frac{(4 \times ((6 + 1) \times (8 \times 5)))}{((9 + 23) \times 70)} := \frac{(4 \times (6 - (1^{85})))}{(((9 + 2) \times 3) + (7 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 \times (1 \times (8 - 5))))}{(9 \times (23 - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times (6 \times (1^{85})))}{(9 + (2 + (37 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times (6 + ((1^8) \times 5)))}{(92 + (3 - (7 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 + ((1^8) + 5)))}{(92 - (3 - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times (6 + (1 - (8 - 5))))}{(9 + (2 + (3 \times (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 \times (6 + (1^{85})))}{(9 - (23 - 70))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 + (1 + (8 - 5))))}{(9 - (2 - (3 + 70)))} := \frac{(4 + ((6 \times 18) - 5))}{((9 \times 23) + (7 - 0))} := \frac{(4 + ((6 + (1 \times 8)) \times 5))}{((9^2) - (3 - 70))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (6 - ((1^8) \times 5)))}{(9 + ((2^3) - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 + (6 - (1 - (8 \times 5))))}{((9 + (2 + 3)) \times (7 - 0))} := \frac{(4 + (6 - (1 - (8 - 5))))}{(9 + ((2^3) + (7 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (6 - (1 \times (8 - 5))))}{((9^2) + (3 - 70))} := \frac{(4 + (6 \times (1 \times (8 - 5))))}{(9 - (2 - (37 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 + (6 + (1 - (8 - 5))))}{(9 - ((2 - 3) \times (7 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (6 + (1 \times (8 - 5))))}{(((9 + 2) \times 3) - (7 - 0))} := \frac{(4 + (6 + (1^{85})))}{(9 + ((2 \times 3) + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 + (6 + (1 + (8 \times 5))))}{(9 + (23 + 70))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (6 + (1 + (8 - 5))))}{(9 - (2 - (3 \times (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 + (6 + (18 \times 5)))}{(9 + (6 + (18 \times 5)))} := \frac{(4 + (61 - (8 - 5)))}{(4 + (61 - (8 - 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (61 + (8 \times 5)))}{((9 - (2 \times 3)) \times 70)} := \frac{(46 - (1 + (8 - 5)))}{(9 + (2 + (3 + 70)))} := \frac{(46 + (1 \times (8 + 5)))}{((9^2) + (37 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(461 - (8 - 5))}{(923 - (7 - 0))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► **48351**
96702

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((4 \times 8) + 3) \times (5 + 1))}{((9 - 6) \times (70 \times 2))} := \frac{(((4 + 8) \times (3 + 5)) + 1)}{((9 \times 6) + (70 \times 2))} := \frac{((4 \times ((8 \times 3) + 5)) + 1)}{(9 \times ((6 + (7 - 0)) \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((4 \times (8 - (3 - 5))) + 1)}{(96 + (7 \times (0 - 2)))} := \frac{(((4 \times (8 - (3 - 5))) - 1)}{(9 + (67 - (0 - 2)))} := \frac{((4 \times (8 \times 3)) + (5 + 1))}{((9 - 6) \times (70 - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((4 \times (8 + (3 + 5))) - 1)}{((9 \times 6) + (70 + 2))} := \frac{(((4 \times (8 + 3)) - (5 + 1))}{(9 + (67 - (0 \times 2)))} := \frac{(((4 \times (83 + 5)) - 1)}{(9 \times (6 + (70 + 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times 83) + (5 \times 1))}{((96 \times (7 - 0)) + 2)} := \frac{((4 \times 83) + (5 + 1))}{((96 - 70)^2)} := \frac{((4 + (8 + 3)) \times (5 + 1))}{(9 \times (6 - (7 \times (0 - 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 + 8) \times (3 \times 51))}{(9 \times (6 \times (70 - 2)))} := \frac{((4 + 8) \times (3 + (5 + 1)))}{((9 - 6) \times (70 + 2))} := \frac{((48 - 3) \times (5 - 1))}{(9 \times ((6 \times (7 - 0)) - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (8 - ((3^5) + 1)))}{(96 \times (7 + (0 - 2)))} := \frac{(4 - (8 - (3 \times (5 \times 1))))}{(9 + (6 + (7 - (0 \times 2))))} := \frac{(4 - (8 - (3 \times (5 - 1))))}{((9 + (6 - (7 - 0))) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (8 - (3 + (5 \times 1))))}{(9 - (6 - (7 + (0 - 2))))} := \frac{(4 - (8 - (3 + (5 - 1))))}{(9 + (6 - (7 - (0 - 2))))} := \frac{(4 - (8 - (3 + 51)))}{((9 - (6 - (7 - 0)))^2)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(4 - (8 - (35 + 1)))}{(9 + (6 + (7^{02})))} &:= \frac{(4 - (8 \times (3 - (5 \times 1))))}{((9 \times 6) + (7 \times (0 - 2)))} &:= \frac{(4 - (8 \times (3 - (5 - 1))))}{(9 + (6 + (7 - (0 - 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (8 + (3 \times (5 + 1))))}{(((9 - 6) \times 70) - 2)} &:= \frac{(4 + (((8 + 3) \times 5) - 1))}{((9 - 67) \times (0 - 2))} &:= \frac{(4 + ((8 \times 3) - (5 + 1)))}{((9 + (6 + (7 - 0))) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + ((8 \times 3) + (5 \times 1)))}{((9 - (6 \times 7)) \times (0 - 2))} &:= \frac{(4 + ((8^3) - (5 + 1)))}{((9 + 6) \times (70 - 2))} &:= \frac{(4 + ((8 - 3) \times (5 + 1)))}{((9 \times 6) - (7 \times (0 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 - (3 - (5 \times 1))))}{(96 - (70 - 2))} &:= \frac{(4 + (8 - (3 + (5 - 1))))}{(9 + (6 - (7 + (0 - 2))))} &:= \frac{(4 + (8 \times (3 \times (5 \times 1))))}{(((9 \times 6) + 70) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 \times (3 + (5 + 1))))}{((9 + (67 - 0)) \times 2)} &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + ((3 \times 5) - 1)))}{(9 - (6 - (7^{02})))} &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + (3 - (5 \times 1))))}{(9 + (6 + (7 + (0 - 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + (3 - (5 + 1))))}{(9 \times ((6 - 7) \times (0 - 2)))} &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + (3 \times (5 \times 1))))}{(9 \times (6 - (7 \times (0 \times 2))))} &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + (3 + (5 + 1))))}{((9 - 6) \times (7 \times (0 + 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + (35 \times 1)))}{(((9 \times 6) - (7 - 0)) \times 2)} &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + (35 + 1)))}{(96 - (7 \times (0 \times 2)))} &:= \frac{(4 + (83 - (5 \times 1)))}{(96 + (70 - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(48 \times (3^{5+1}))}{9 \times 6^{7-02}} &:= \frac{(48 \times (3 + (5 + 1)))}{(96 \times (7 - (0 - 2)))} &:= \frac{(48 \times ((3 \times 5) - 1))}{(96 \times (7 \times (0 + 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(48 + (35 + 1))}{(96 + (70 + 2))} &:= \frac{48 + 351}{96 + 702} &:= \frac{4835 + 1}{9670 + 2} \\
 &:= \frac{4835 - 1}{9670 - 2}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.51 53 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10674}{85392} &:= \frac{(((1^{06}) + 7) \times 4)}{(8 + (5 + (3 \times (9^2))))} &:= \frac{(((10 + 6) \times 7) - 4)}{(853 + (9 + 2))} &:= \frac{(((10 - 6) \times 7) - 4)}{(8 + ((5 - 3) \times 92))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((10 - 6)^7) \times 4)}{8^{5 \times 3 - 9} \times 2} &:= \frac{(((1 - (0 - (6 + 7))) \times 4)}{((8^5 - 3) \times (9 - 2))} &:= \frac{(((1 - (0 - 6)) \times (7 + 4))}{((85 + 3) \times (9 - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((1^{06}) \times (7 \times 4))}{((85 + (3 \times 9)) \times 2)} &:= \frac{(((1^{06}) \times (7 + 4))}{(((8 + (5 - 3)) \times 9) - 2)} &:= \frac{(((1^{06}) \times 74)}{(8 \times (((5 + 3) \times 9) + 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((1^{06}) + (7 \times 4))}{(8 \times (5 + ((3 + 9) \times 2)))} &:= \frac{(((1^{06}) + (7 + 4))}{(8 + ((5 + 39) \times 2))} &:= \frac{(((1 + (0 - (6 - 7))) \times 4)}{(8 + ((5 + 3) \times (9 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((1 + (0 - (6 - 7)))^4)}{(8 + (5 \times ((3 + 9) \times 2)))} &:= \frac{(((10 \times (6 + 7)) + 4)}{(8 \times (53 + (9^2)))} &:= \frac{(((10 \times 6) + (7 \times 4))}{(8 \times ((5 + 39) \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((10 \times 6) + (7^4))}{(8 - (5 - ((3^9) + 2)))} &:= \frac{(((10 + (6 + 7)) \times 4)}{(((85 - 3) \times 9) - 2)} &:= \frac{(((10 + (6 - 7)) \times 4)}{(8 \times ((5 - 3) \times (9 \times 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - ((6 \times 7) - 4)))}{((8 + 5) \times ((3 + 9) \times 2))} &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (6 - (7 - 4))))}{(8 - (5 - ((3 \times 9) + 2)))} &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (6 \times (7 - 4))))}{(8 \times (5 + (3 + (9 + 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (6^{7-4})))}{(8 \times ((5^3) + 92))} &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (6 + (7 \times 4))))}{(8 \times (53 - (9 \times 2)))} &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (6 + (7 - 4))))}{((8 + (5 + (3 \times 9))) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (67 - 4)))}{(8 \times ((5 + (3 \times 9)) \times 2))} &:= \frac{(1 - (0 \times (6 - 74)))}{8^{5+3-9+2}} &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - 674))}{(8 + 5392)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 - (6 - (7 \times 4))))}{(8 \times ((5 - (3 - 9)) \times 2))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 - (6 - (7 + 4))))}{(8 - (5 - (39 - 2)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((6 \times 7) + 4)))}{(8 \times (5 + (39 + 2)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((6 \times 7) - 4)))}{(8 \times (5 + (3 \times (9 + 2))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (6 - (7 - 4))))}{(8 - (5 - (3 \times (9 - 2))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (6 \times (7 + 4))))}{(((85 \times 3) + 9) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (6 \times (7 - 4))))}{(8 + ((5^3) + (9 + 2)))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (6 + (7 \times 4))))}{(8 \times ((5 + (3 + 9)) \times 2))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (6 + (7 + 4))))}{(8 \times (5 - ((3 - 9) \times 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (6 + (7 - 4))))}{(8 \times (5 - (3 - (9 - 2))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (67 \times 4)))}{(8 \times (((5^3) + 9) \times 2))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (67 + 4)))}{(8 \times (53 + (9 \times 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + ((0 - (6 - 7))^4))}{(8 + ((5 \times 3) - (9 - 2)))} := \frac{(1 + (0 - (6 - (7 \times 4))))}{((8 \times 5) + ((3 + 9)^2))} := \frac{(1 + (0 - (6 - (7 + 4))))}{(8 - (5 \times (3 - (9 + 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (6 - 74)))}{((8 - (5 - 3)) \times 92)} := \frac{(10 - ((6 - 7) \times 4))}{(8 \times ((5 - 3) \times (9 - 2)))} := \frac{(10 - (6 - (7 + 4)))}{(8 \times (5 + (3 + (9 - 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 - (6 - (7 - 4)))}{((8 - (5 - 3)) \times 9)} := \frac{(10 \times (6 - (7 - 4)))}{(8 \times (5 + ((3 \times 9) - 2)))} := \frac{(10 \times (6 + 74))}{((8 + ((5 + 3) \times 9))^2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 + ((6 \times 7) - 4))}{(8 \times (((5 \times 3) + 9) \times 2))} := \frac{(10 + ((6 + 7) \times 4))}{(8 \times ((5 \times (3 + 9)) + 2))} := \frac{(10 + (6 - (7 - 4)))}{(8 \times (5 - (3 - (9 + 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 + (6 + (7 \times 4)))}{(8 \times ((5^3) - (9^2)))} := \frac{(10 + (67 - 4))}{(8 + (((5 \times 3) + 9)^2))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► **13845**
27690

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((1 + 3)^8) \times (4^5))}{(((2 \times 7) - 6)^9 + 0)} := \frac{((1 - ((3 - 8) \times 4)) \times 5)}{(2 \times (7 \times (6 + (9 - 0))))} := \frac{((1 - (3 - 8)) \times (4^5))}{((2^7) \times (6 + 90))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1^3) \times (8 - (4 - 5)))}{(2 \times ((7 - 6) \times (9 - 0)))} := \frac{((1^3) \times (8 \times (4 + 5)))}{(((2 + 7) \times 6) + 90)} := \frac{((1^3) \times (8 \times 45))}{(((2 \times 7) - 6) \times 90)} \\
 &:= \frac{((1^3) + (84 + 5))}{(2 \times ((7 - 6) \times 90))} := \frac{((1 + 38) \times (4 + 5))}{((2 + 76) \times (9 - 0))} := \frac{((13 \times 8) + (4 - 5))}{(2 \times (7 + (6 + 90)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((13 + 8) \times 45)}{((27 - 6) \times 90)} := \frac{((138 \times 4) - 5)}{(2 \times (7 + (6 \times 90)))} := \frac{(1 - ((3 - (8 + 4)) \times 5))}{(2 + ((7 - 6) \times 90))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (3 - ((8 + 4) \times 5)))}{((2 \times (7 + 6)) + 90)} := \frac{(1 - (3 - (8 + (4 + 5))))}{(27 - (6 - (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 - (3 - (8 + (4 - 5))))}{(2 - (7 - (6 + (9 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (3 - (8 + 45)))}{(2 \times ((7 \times 6) + (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 - (3 - (84 + 5)))}{((2 \times (7 \times 6)) + 90)} := \frac{(1 - (3 \times (8 - (4 \times 5))))}{(1 - (3 + (8 \times (4 - 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (3 \times (8 \times (4 - 5))))}{(2 - ((7 \times 6) - 90))} := \frac{(1 - (3 \times (8 - 45)))}{((2^7) + (6 + 90))} := \frac{(1 - (3 + (8 \times (4 - 5))))}{(2 + (7 - (6 - (9 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - ((7 \times 6) - 90))}{(1 \times (((3 + 8) \times 4) + 5))} := \frac{((2^7) + (6 + 90))}{(1 \times ((3 \times (8 \times 4)) - 5))} := \frac{(2 + (7 - (6 - (9 - 0))))}{(1 \times ((3 \times 8) + (4 + 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (7 - (6 - 90)))}{(1 \times ((38 + 4) \times 5))} := \frac{(2 \times (7 - (6 - 90)))}{(1 \times (3 - (8 - (4 + 5))))} := \frac{(2 \times ((7 \times 6) - (9 - 0)))}{(1 \times (3 \times (8 + (4 \times 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - 7) \times (6 - 90)}{(1 \times (3 \times (8 + (4 - 5))))} := \frac{(2 \times (7 + (6 - (9 - 0))))}{(1 \times (3 + ((8 \times 4) - 5)))} := \frac{(2 + (76 + 90))}{(1 \times (3 + (8 - (4 - 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(27 + (6 + (9 - 0)))}{(1 \times (3 + (8 + (4 \times 5))))} := \frac{(((2 - 7) \times 6) + 90)}{(1 \times (3 + (8 + (4 - 5))))} := \frac{(2 + (7 + (6 + (9 - 0))))}{(1 \times (38 - (4 - 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times 76) - 90}{1^{3845}} := \frac{(2 \times (7 - (6 - (9 - 0))))}{(1 + ((3 \times (8 - 4)) - 5))} := \frac{(2 + (7 + (69 - 0)))}{(1 + ((3 \times 8) + (4 \times 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{2 \times (7 - 6)^9 + 0}{(1 + ((3 \times 8) + (4 + 5)))} := \frac{2^{7+6-9+0}}{(1 + ((3 + (8 - 4)) \times 5))} := \frac{(2 - (7 - 6)) \times 90}{(1 + (3 - (8 - (4 \times 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times 7) + (6 \times (9 - 0))}{(1 + (3 \times ((8 - 4) \times 5)))} := \frac{((27 \times 6) - 90)}{(1 + (3 \times (8 + (4 \times 5))))} := \frac{((2^7) - (6 + 90))}{(1 + (3 \times (8 + (4 - 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (7 + (6 \times (9 - 0))))}{(1 + (3 + (8 - (4 + 5))))} := \frac{(2 \times (76 + (9 - 0)))}{(1 + (3 + (8 \times (4 + 5))))} := \frac{(2 \times (7 + (6 + (9 - 0))))}{(1 + (3 + (8 + (4 \times 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (7 + (6 - (9 - 0))))}{(2 \times (7 + (69 - 0)))} := \frac{(2 \times (7 + (69 - 0)))}{(2 - (7 - (69 - 0)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(1 + (3 + (84 + 5)))}{(276 - 90)} &:= \frac{(1 + (38 \times (4 + 5)))}{(2 + (76 \times (9 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (38 + (4 + 5)))}{(27 + (69 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + 3845)}{(2 + 7690)} &:= \frac{(13 \times (8 - (4 - 5)))}{(2 \times ((7 + 6) \times (9 - 0)))} &:= \frac{13^{8-4+5}}{2 \times (7 + 6)^9 + 0} \\ &:= \frac{(138 \times (4 + 5))}{(276 \times (9 - 0))} &:= \frac{(138 + 45)}{(276 + 90)} \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{14835}{29670}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(((1^4) + 8) \times (3^5))}{(2 \times ((9 - 6)^7 + 0))} &:= \frac{(((1 + 4) \times 8) + (3 - 5))}{((2 \times (9 - 6)) + 70)} &:= \frac{(((1 - 4) \times 8) + (3^5))}{((2 \times 9) + (6 \times 70))} \\ &:= \frac{((1 - (4 - 8)) \times 35)}{((2 + (9 - 6)) \times 70)} &:= \frac{((1^4) \times ((8 \times 3) - 5))}{((2 \times (9 \times 6)) - 70)} &:= \frac{((1^4) \times (8 \times 35))}{((2^{9-6}) \times 70)} \\ &:= \frac{(((1^4) + (83 + 5))}{(2 \times (96 - (7 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(((1 + (4 \times (8 - 3))) \times 5)}{(2 \times ((9 + 6) \times (7 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(((1 + (4 + (8 + 3)))^5)}{((2^{9-6})^7 + 0)} \\ &:= \frac{(((1 + (4 + (8 - 3))) \times 5)}{((2 \times (9 + 6)) + 70)} &:= \frac{((14 + (8 \times 3)) \times 5)}{(2 + (9 \times (6 \times (7 - 0))))} &:= \frac{((14 - 8) \times 35)}{(2 \times ((9 - 6) \times 70))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - ((4 - (8 - 3)) \times 5))}{(2 + (9 - (6 - (7 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(1 - (4 - ((8 + 3) \times 5)))}{((29 \times 6) - 70)} &:= \frac{(1 - (4 - ((8 - 3) \times 5)))}{(2 \times (9 + (6 + (7 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (4 - (8 \times (3 \times 5))))}{(2 \times (9 \times (6 + (7 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(1 - (4 - (8 \times (3 + 5))))}{((2 \times 96) - 70)} &:= \frac{(1 - (4 - (8 \times 35)))}{((2^9) + (6 \times (7 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (4 - (8 + (3 - 5))))}{(2 - (9 - (6 + (7 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(1 - (4 - (83 + 5)))}{(2 \times (9 + (6 + 70)))} &:= \frac{(1 - (48 - (3^5)))}{((2 + (9 \times 6)) \times (7 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times ((4 \times (8 + 3)) - 5))}{(2 + (9 + (67 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((4 \times 83) + 5))}{(2 + (96 \times (7 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((4 - 8) \times (3 - 5)))}{(2 \times (9 + (6 - (7 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 + (8 - (3 - 5))))}{(2 + (96 - 70))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 + (8 \times (3 \times 5))))}{(2 \times ((9 \times 6) + 70))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 + (8 \times (3 + 5))))}{(((2 + 9) \times 6) + 70)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 + (8 + (3 - 5))))}{(2 \times (9 - (6 - (7 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 + (8 + 35)))}{(2 \times ((9 \times 6) - (7 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (48 + (3 \times 5)))}{(2 + ((9 \times 6) + 70))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (((4 + 8) \times 3) + 5))}{(((2 \times 9) - 6) \times (7 - 0))} &:= \frac{(1 + ((4 \times (8 - 3)) + 5))}{(2 \times (96 - 70))} &:= \frac{(1 + ((4 + (8 + 3)) \times 5))}{(2 \times (9 + (67 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + ((4 + (8 - 3)) \times 5))}{((2^9) - (6 \times 70))} &:= \frac{(1 + ((4 - 8) \times (3 - 5)))}{(2 - ((9 \times 6) - 70))} &:= \frac{(1 + (4 - (8 - (3 \times 5))))}{(2 + (9 + (6 + (7 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (4 - (8 - (3 + 5))))}{(2 + (9 + (6 - (7 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(1 + (4 - (8 \times (3 - 5))))}{(2 \times ((9 - 6) \times (7 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (4 \times (8 - (3 - 5))))}{((2 \times 9) - (6 - 70))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (4 + ((8 - 3) \times 5)))}{(2 - (9 - (67 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (4 + (8 - (3 - 5))))}{(29 - (6 - (7 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (4 + (8 + (3 \times 5))))}{((2^{9-6}) \times (7 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (4 + (8 + 35)))}{(29 + (67 - 0))} &:= \frac{(1 + (4 + (83 \times 5)))}{(((2 \times 9) - 6) \times 70)} &:= \frac{(1 + (4 + 835))}{(((2 \times 9) + 6) \times 70)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (48 - (3 - 5)))}{(2 \times (9 + (6 \times (7 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(1 + (48 + 35))}{(2 + (96 + 70))} &:= \frac{(1 + 4835)}{(2 + 9670)} \\ &:= \frac{(14 \times (8 + (3 + 5)))}{((2^9) + (6 - 70))} &:= \frac{(14 + (8 \times 35))}{((2^9) + (6 + 70))} &:= \frac{(14 + (83 \times 5))}{(2 \times (9 + (6 \times 70)))} \\ &:= \frac{148 + 35}{296 + 70} &:= \frac{148 - 35}{296 - 70} \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{38145}{76290}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(((3 \times 8) + (1 + 4)) \times 5)}{((7 - 6) \times 290)} &:= \frac{((3 - (8 - 14)) \times 5)}{(((7 - 6)^2) \times 90)} &:= \frac{((3 \times ((8 - 1) \times 4)) + 5)}{(((7 + 6)^2) + (9 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{((3 \times (8 - (1^4))) + 5)}{(7 + ((6^2) + (9 - 0)))} &:= \frac{((3 \times (8 \times (1^4))) + 5)}{(76 - (2 \times (9 - 0)))} &:= \frac{((3 \times (8 + 1)) + (4 \times 5))}{(76 + (2 \times (9 - 0)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{((3 \times 81) + (4 + 5))}{(7 \times ((6 + 2) \times (9 - 0)))} := \frac{((3 \times 81) - 45)}{(((7 \times 6) + 2) \times (9 - 0))} := \frac{((3 + (8 \times 1)) \times 45)}{((7 + (6 - 2)) \times 90)} \\
 & := \frac{((3 + (8 + (1 + 4))) \times 5)}{(((7 + 6)^2) - (9 - 0))} := \frac{((3 + (8 - 1)) \times (4 + 5))}{((7 - 6) \times (2 \times 90))} := \frac{((3 + 8) \times (1 + (4 \times 5)))}{(7 \times (6 \times (2 + (9 - 0))))} \\
 & := \frac{((3 + 8) \times (1 - (4 - 5)))}{((76 \times 2) + 90)} := \frac{((3 + 81) \times 45)}{(7 \times (6 \times (2 \times 90)))} := \frac{((38 - 1) \times (4 + 5))}{((76 - 2) \times (9 - 0))} \\
 & := \frac{((381 - 4) \times 5)}{((7 + 6) \times 290)} := \frac{(3 - (8 - (1 \times (4 \times 5))))}{(7 - (6 - (29 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 - (8 - (1 \times (4 + 5))))}{(7 - (6 + (2 - (9 - 0))))} \\
 & := \frac{((3 - (8 - (1 + (4 + 5))))}{(3 - (8 - (14 \times 5)))} := \frac{(3 - (8 - (1 \times (4 \times 5))))}{(3 - (8 \times (1 + (4 - 5))))} \\
 & := \frac{(7 + ((6 \times 2) - (9 - 0)))}{(3 - (8 + (1 - (4 \times 5))))} := \frac{((7 \times 6) - (2 - 90))}{(3 - (8 + (1 - 45)))} := \frac{(7 + (6 + (2 - (9 - 0))))}{(3 \times ((8 \times (1 \times 4)) + 5))} \\
 & := \frac{(7 + ((6 \times 2) + (9 - 0)))}{(3 \times ((8 \times 14) + 5))} := \frac{(7 + (62 + (9 - 0)))}{(3 \times ((8 + (1 \times 4)) \times 5))} := \frac{((7 \times 6) + (2 \times 90))}{(3 \times ((8 + (1^4)) \times 5))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 \times ((8 \times 14) + 5))}{((76 + 2) \times (9 - 0))} := \frac{(3 \times ((8 + (1 \times 4)) \times 5))}{(((7 \times 6) - 2) \times (9 - 0))} := \frac{(3 \times ((8 + (1^4)) \times 5))}{((7 - (6 - 2)) \times 90)} \\
 & := \frac{(3 \times (8 - ((1^4) + 5)))}{(7 - (6 - (2 + (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(3 \times (8 - (1 - (4 \times 5))))}{((7 \times (6^2)) - 90)} := \frac{(3 \times (8 + (1 - (4 - 5))))}{(7 + (62 - (9 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 \times (8 + (1 \times (4 \times 5))))}{(7 \times (6 + (2 \times (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(3 \times (8 + (1 \times (4 - 5))))}{(7 + (6 + (29 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 \times (8 + (1 + (4 \times 5))))}{((7 \times (6 \times 2)) + 90)} \\
 & := \frac{(3 \times (81 - (4 \times 5)))}{(76 + 290)} := \frac{(3 \times (81 + 45))}{(7 \times (6 \times (2 \times (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(3 + ((8 - (1 - 4)) \times 5))}{(((7 + 6) \times 2) + 90)} \\
 & := \frac{(3 + ((8 - 1) \times 45))}{(7 + (629 - 0))} := \frac{(3 + (8 - (1 - (4 - 5))))}{((7 - 6) \times (2 \times (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 + (8 - (1 \times (4 + 5))))}{(7 - ((6 \times 2) - (9 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 + (8 - (1 \times (4 - 5))))}{(7 + (6 + (2 + (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(3 + (8 - (1 + (4 + 5))))}{(7 + (6 - (2 + (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(3 + (8 \times (1 + (4 \times 5))))}{((7 \times (6^2)) + 90)} \\
 & := \frac{(3 + (8 \times (1 - (4 - 5))))}{((7 \times 6) + (2 + 90))} := \frac{(3 + (8 + ((1^4) + 5)))}{(7 + ((6^2) - (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 + (8 + (1 \times (4 \times 5))))}{((76 \times 2) - 90)} \\
 & := \frac{(3 + (8 + (1 \times (4 - 5))))}{(7 + (6 - (2 - (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(3 + (8 + (1 + (4^5))))}{(7 \times (6 + 290))} := \frac{(38 - (1 - (4 + 5)))}{((7 - 6) \times (2 + 90))} \\
 & := \frac{(38 - (1 - 45))}{(76 - (2 - 90))} := \frac{(38 + (1 + (4 \times 5)))}{((7 \times (6 - 2)) + 90)} := \frac{381 \times (4 + 5)}{762 \times 9 + 0} \\
 & := \frac{381 + 45}{762 + 90} := \frac{381 - 45}{762 - 90}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{48135}{96270} := \frac{(((4 \times (8 \times 1)) + 3) \times 5)}{((9 - (6 - 2)) \times 70)} := \frac{(((4 + (8 - 1)) \times 3) + 5)}{(((9 - 6) \times 2) + 70)} := \frac{((4 \times (8 - (1 - 3))) - 5)}{((9 - (6 + 2)) \times 70)}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(((4 \times (8 \times (1 \times 3))) - 5)}{(9 \times 6) + (2^7 + 0))} := \frac{(((4 \times (8 + (1^3))) + 5)}{(96 - (2 \times (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(((4 \times (8 + (1 + 3))) + 5)}{(9 \times (6 - 2)) + 70)} \\
 & := \frac{(((4 \times (8 + 1)) + 35)}{(9 \times (6 + 2)) + 70)} := \frac{(((4 \times (8 + 13)) + 5)}{(9 \times (6 \times 2)) + 70)} := \frac{(((4 \times (8 - 1)) + 35)}{(9 \times 6) + (2 + 70))} \\
 & := \frac{(((4 \times 8) + (13 \times 5))}{((9 \times 6) + (2 \times 70))} := \frac{(((4 + (8 - (1^3))) \times 5)}{(96 + (2 \times (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(((4 + (8 \times 13)) \times 5)}{((9 + 6) \times (2 + 70))} \\
 & := \frac{(((4 + (8 + (1 - 3))) \times 5)}{(((9 + 6) \times 2) + 70)} := \frac{(((4 + (8 + 1)) \times 35)}{((9 + (6 - 2)) \times 70)} := \frac{(((48 \times (1 + 3)) + 5)}{((9 \times (6^2)) + 70)} \\
 & := \frac{(((48 + 1) \times (3 \times 5))}{((9 + (6 \times 2)) \times 70)} := \frac{(4 - (8 - ((1^3) \times 5)))}{((9 \times (6 + 2)) - 70)} := \frac{(4 - (8 - ((1^3) + 5)))}{(9 - ((6 \times 2) - (7 - 0)))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 - (8 - (1 + 35)))}{(9 + (62 - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 - (8 - (13 \times 5)))}{((96 \times 2) - 70)} := \frac{(4 - (8 \times ((1 - 3) \times 5)))}{(96 + (2 + 70))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(4 - (8 \times (1 - (3 \times 5))))}{(((9+6)^2) + (7-0))} := \frac{(4 - (8 \times (1 + (3 - 5))))}{(9 + (6 + (2 + (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 - (8 + (1 - (3 + 5))))}{(9 + (6 - (2 + (7 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (8 - 135))}{((96 \times 2) + 70)} := \frac{(4 \times ((8 \times (1 + 3)) - 5))}{((9 - 6) \times (2 + 70))} := \frac{(4 \times ((8 + 1) \times 35))}{(9 \times ((6 - 2) \times 70))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (8 - (1 - (3 - 5))))}{((9 \times 6) - (2 \times (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times (8 \times ((1^3) + 5)))}{((9 - 6) \times (2^7 + 0))} := \frac{(4 \times (8 + ((1 + 3) \times 5)))}{(96 + (2^7 + 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (81 \times 35))}{(9 \times ((6^2) \times 70))} := \frac{(4 \times (81 + (3^5)))}{(96 \times (27 - 0))} := \frac{4^{8+1-3-5}}{(9 - (6 + (2 - (7 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + ((8 - (1^3)) \times 5))}{(9 + (62 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 + ((8 + (1 - 3)) \times 5))}{((9 \times 6) + (2 \times (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 + ((8 + 13) \times 5))}{(((9 + 6)^2) - (7 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + ((81 \times 3) + 5))}{(9 \times ((6 + 2) \times (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 + (8 - ((1^3) \times 5)))}{(9 + ((6 \times 2) - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 + (8 - ((1^3) + 5)))}{(9 - (6 - (2 + (7 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 - (1 - (3 \times 5))))}{(9 + ((6^2) + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 + (8 - (1 - (3 + 5))))}{(9 + ((6^2) - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 + (8 - (1 \times (3 - 5))))}{(9 + ((6 \times 2) + (7 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 \times (1 - (3 - 5))))}{(962 + 70)} := \frac{(4 + (8 + ((1^3) - 5)))}{(((9 - 6)^2) + (7 - 0))} := \frac{(4 + (8 + (1 - (3 + 5))))}{(9 + (6 + (2 - (7 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + (1 - (3 - 5))))}{(9 - (6 - (27 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 + (8 + (1 \times (3 - 5))))}{(9 + (6 - (2 - (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 + (8 + (1 + (3 + 5))))}{(9 + (6 + (27 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(48 - (1 - 35))}{(96 - (2 - 70))} := \frac{(48 \times ((1 + 3) \times 5))}{((9 + 6) \times (2^7 + 0))} := \frac{(48 \times (1 + (3 + 5)))}{(96 \times (2 + (7 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(48 + 135)}{(96 + 270)} := \frac{(481 - 35)}{(962 - 70)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► **63018**
94527

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((6 \times (3^{01})) + 8)}{(((9 - 4) \times 5) + (2 \times 7))} := \frac{((6 \times (3 + (0 - 1))) + 8)}{(9 - (4 + (5 \times (2 - 7))))} := \frac{((6 \times (30 \times 1)) + 8)}{(94 \times ((5 \times 2) - 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 \times (30 + 1)) - 8)}{(((9 - 4) \times 52) + 7)} := \frac{((6 \times (30 - 1)) + 8)}{((9 + 4) \times ((5 - 2) \times 7))} := \frac{((6 \times 30) + 18)}{(9 \times ((4 \times (5 \times 2)) - 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6^{3-01}) \times 8)}{((9 \times 45) + 27)} := \frac{((6^{3-01}) + 8)}{(9 + ((4^5-2) - 7))} := \frac{((6^{3-01}) - 8)}{((9 + (4 - (5 + 2))) \times 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{((6^3) \times (0 - (1 - 8)))}{(((9 + (4 + 5))^2) \times 7)} := \frac{((6 + 30) \times 18)}{(945 + 27)} := \frac{((6 - 30) \times (1 - 8))}{(9 + ((4 + 5) \times 27))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 - ((3 \times (0 \times 1)) - 8))}{(9 + (4 \times ((5 \times 2) - 7)))} := \frac{(6 - (3 - (0 - (1^8))))}{(9 + (4 - (5 - (2 - 7))))} := \frac{(6 - (3 \times (0 - (1 \times 8))))}{(9 + (4 + (5 + 27)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 - (3 \times (0 \times 18)))}{(9 - (4 \times (5 + (2 - 7))))} := \frac{(6 - (3 \times (0 - 18)))}{((9 - (4 - 5)) \times (2 + 7))} := \frac{(6 \times ((3 \times (0 \times 1)) + 8))}{(9 \times (4 - (5 - (2 + 7))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times ((3 + (0 - 1))^8))}{((9 + (4 + 5)) \times (2^7))} := \frac{(6 \times (3 - (0 - (1 \times 8))))}{(9 \times (((4 + 5) \times 2) - 7))} := \frac{(6 \times (3 - (0 - (1^8))))}{(9 \times (4 - (5 + (2 - 7))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (3 - (0 - (1 + 8))))}{(9 \times (4 \times ((5 \times 2) - 7)))} := \frac{(6 \times (3 - (0 \times 18)))}{(9 - (4 + (5 - 27)))} := \frac{(6 \times (3 - (0 - 18)))}{(9 + (4 \times (5 \times (2 + 7))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (3 \times (0 + (1 \times 8))))}{((9 + (4 - 5)) \times 27)} := \frac{(6 \times (3 \times (0 + 18)))}{(9 \times (45 + (2 + 7)))} := \frac{(6 \times (3^{-01+8}))}{((9^4) \times ((5 \times 2) - 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (3^{01 \times 8}))}{(9^{4 \times (5-2)-7})} := \frac{(6 \times (3 + (0 - (1^8))))}{(9 - ((4 - 5) \times (2 + 7)))} := \frac{(6 \times (30 - (1 \times 8)))}{(9 \times (4 + ((5^2) - 7)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (30 - (1^8)))}{(9 \times (4 - (5 \times (2 - 7))))} := \frac{(6 \times (30 \times 18))}{(9 \times (4 \times (5 \times 27)))} := \frac{(6 \times (30 \times (1^8)))}{((9 - (4 - 5)) \times 27)} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (30 + (1 \times 8)))}{((94 \times 5) - (2^7))} := \frac{(6 \times (30 + (1^8)))}{(9 \times (45 - (2 \times 7)))} := \frac{(6 \times (30 + (1 - 8)))}{(9 \times (4 + (5 + (2 \times 7))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{6^3 + 0 \times 18}{(9 \times (4 + (5 + 27)))} & := \frac{6^{3+0-1^8}}{(9 - (4 - ((5 + 2) \times 7)))} & := \frac{(6 + ((3 - (0 - 1)) \times 8))}{(((9 + (4 - 5))^2) - 7)} \\
 & := \frac{(6 + ((3 + (0 - 1)) \times 8))}{((9 \times 4) - ((5 \times 2) - 7))} & := \frac{(6 + (3 - (0 - (1^8))))}{(9 - (4 - (5 - (2 - 7))))} & := \frac{(6 + (3 + (0 - (1 - 8))))}{(9 - (4 - (5 + (2 \times 7))))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 + (30 \times (1 \times 8)))}{(9 - (4 - (52 \times 7)))} & := \frac{(6 + (30 \times (1 + 8)))}{(9 + (45 \times (2 + 7)))} & := \frac{(6 + (30 + 18))}{(9 + (4 \times ((5^2) - 7)))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 + 3018)}{(9 + 4527)} & := \frac{(63 - (0 - (1 - 8)))}{((9 - (4 - (5 + 2))) \times 7)} & := \frac{(63 \times (0 + (1 \times 8)))}{(9 \times (4 \times ((5 - 2) \times 7)))} \\
 & := \frac{(63 + (0 - (1^8)))}{(9 + (4 \times ((5 - 2) \times 7)))} & := \frac{(63 + (0 - (1 - 8)))}{((9 - (4 - (5 \times 2))) \times 7)} & := \frac{(630 - (1 \times 8))}{((94 \times (5 \times 2)) - 7)} \\
 & := \frac{(630 \times (1 + 8))}{(945 \times (2 + 7))} & := \frac{(630 - 18)}{(945 - 27)}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.52 54 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10647}{95823} & := \frac{(((1^{06}) + 4)^7)}{9 \times 5^{8+2-3}} & := \frac{((1 - (0 - (6 + 4))) \times 7)}{(9 \times ((5 \times (8 \times 2)) - 3))} & := \frac{((1 - (0 - (6 - 4))) \times 7)}{(9 \times (5 + (8 + (2^3))))} \\
 & := \frac{((1^{06}) \times (4 \times 7))}{((9 + 5) \times ((8 - 2) \times 3))} & := \frac{((1^{06}) \times (4 + 7))}{(9 + (5 + (82 + 3)))} & := \frac{((1^{06}) \times 47)}{(9 \times ((5 \times (8 + 2)) - 3))} \\
 & := \frac{((1^{06}) + (4 \times 7))}{(9 \times (((5 + 8) \times 2) + 3))} & := \frac{((1^{06}) + (4 + 7))}{(9 \times (5 + (8 + (2 - 3))))} & := \frac{((1^{06}) + 47)}{(((9 - (5 - 8))^2) \times 3)} \\
 & := \frac{((10^{6-4}) + 7)}{(958 + (2 + 3))} & := \frac{((10^{6-4}) - 7)}{(9 + (5 + 823))} & := \frac{((10 + (6 - 4)) \times 7)}{(9 \times (5 + (82 - 3)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - ((0 \times 64) - 7))}{(9 \times (5 + (8 - (2 + 3))))} & := \frac{(1 - (0 - ((6 \times 4) + 7)))}{((9 + (5 + 82)) \times 3)} & := \frac{(1 - (0 - ((6 - 4) \times 7)))}{(9 \times (5 \times (8 - (2 + 3))))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (0 - (6 - (4 - 7))))}{(9 \times (5 \times (8 - (2 \times 3))))} & := \frac{(1 - (0 - (6 + (4 \times 7))))}{(9 \times (5 \times (8 + (2 - 3))))} & := \frac{(1 - (0 - (6 + (4 - 7))))}{(9 + ((5 \times (8 - 2)) - 3))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (0 - (64 + 7)))}{(9 \times (5 + ((8^2) + 3)))} & := \frac{(1 - (0 - (64 - 7)))}{((95 - 8) \times (2 \times 3))} & := \frac{(1 - (0 \times (6 - 47)))}{(9 - (5 \times (8 - (2^3))))} \\
 & := \frac{(9 + 5823)}{(1 \times (0 - (6 - (4 + 7))))} & := \frac{(9 \times (5 + (8 - (2 \times 3))))}{(1 \times (0 - (6 \times (4 - 7))))} & := \frac{(9 + (5 + (8 \times 23)))}{(1 \times (0 - (6 - 47)))} \\
 & := \frac{(9 + (5 + (8 + 23)))}{(1 \times (0 + ((6 \times 4) + 7)))} & := \frac{(9 \times (5 + (8 + (2 + 3))))}{(1 \times (0 + ((6 + 4) \times 7)))} & := \frac{(9 \times ((5 \times 8) - (2 - 3)))}{(1 \times (0 + ((6 - 4) \times 7)))} \\
 & := \frac{(95 + (8 \times 23))}{(1 \times (0 + (6 - (4 - 7))))} & := \frac{(9 \times (5 \times (8 + (2 \times 3))))}{(1 \times (0 + (6 \times (4 \times 7))))} & := \frac{(9 \times (5 + (8 - (2 - 3))))}{(1 \times (0 + (6 \times (4^7))))} \\
 & := \frac{9^{5-8+2+3}}{(1 \times (0 + (6 \times (4 + 7))))} & := \frac{(9 \times ((58 - 2) \times 3))}{(1 \times (0 + (6 + (4 \times 7))))} & := \frac{((9 + (5 + 82))^3)}{(1 \times (0 + (6 + (4 + 7))))} \\
 & := \frac{(9 \times (5 + ((8^2) - 3)))}{(1 \times (0 + (6 + (4 - 7))))} & := \frac{(9 \times ((5 \times 8) - (2 \times 3)))}{(1 \times (0 + (6 + 47)))} & := \frac{(9 \times ((5 \times 8) - 23))}{(1 \times (0 + (64 - 7)))} \\
 & := \frac{(9 + (5 + (8 + (2 + 3))))}{(1 + (0 - (6 - (4 \times 7))))} & := \frac{(9 \times (5 + (8 \times (2 \times 3))))}{(1 + (0 - (6 - (4 + 7))))} & := \frac{(9 \times (58 + (2 - 3)))}{(1 + (0 - (6 \times (4 - 7))))} \\
 & := \frac{(9 \times (5 + ((8 - 2) \times 3)))}{(10 \times (6 - (4 - 7)))} & := \frac{(9 + (5 \times (8 - (2 - 3))))}{(10 \times (6 + (4 - 7)))} & := \frac{(9 \times (5 + (8 + (2 \times 3))))}{(10 + ((6 + 4) \times 7))} \\
 & := \frac{(9 \times (5 + (82 + 3)))}{(9 \times (5 + (82 + 3)))} & := \frac{(9 + ((5 + 82) \times 3))}{(9 + ((5 + 82) \times 3))} & := \frac{(9 \times (5 \times (8 + (2^3))))}{(9 \times (5 \times (8 + (2^3))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(10 + ((6 - 4) \times 7))}{(9 + ((5 + (8^2)) \times 3))} &:= \frac{(10 + (6 + (4 + 7)))}{(9 \times ((5 \times (8 - 2)) - 3))} &:= \frac{(10 + (6 + (4 - 7)))}{(9 \times (5 - (8 \times (2 - 3))))} \\ &:= \frac{(10 + (6 + 47))}{(9 \times ((5 + (8 \times 2)) \times 3))} &:= \frac{(10 + (64 + 7))}{(9^{5-8+2 \times 3})} &:= \frac{(106 - (4 \times 7))}{(9 \times ((5 + 8) \times (2 \times 3)))} \\ &:= \frac{(106 - (4 + 7))}{(9 \times (5 \times ((8 \times 2) + 3)))} &:= \frac{(106 - (4 - 7))}{(958 + 23)} &:= \frac{(106 - 47)}{(9 \times (58 - (2 - 3)))} \end{aligned}$$

► **16485**
32970

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(((1 + 6) \times 48) - 5)}{(32 + (9 \times 70))} &:= \frac{(((1 + 64) \times 8) + 5)}{(((3 \times 2) + 9) \times 70)} &:= \frac{(((1 - (6 - (4 \times 8)))^5)}{(3 \times (2 \times (9^7 + 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(((1 - (6 - (4 + 8))) \times 5)}{((3 - (2 - 9)) \times (7 - 0))} &:= \frac{((1^{64}) \times (8 \times 5))}{(3 - (2 - (9 + 70)))} &:= \frac{((1^6) \times 485)}{((3 - 2) \times 970)} \\ &:= \frac{((1^6) + (48 + 5))}{(3 \times (29 + (7 - 0)))} &:= \frac{((1 + 6) \times ((4 \times 8) - 5))}{(3 \times (2 \times (9 \times (7 - 0))))} &:= \frac{((1 + 6) \times (4 \times (8 \times 5)))}{((3 + 29) \times 70)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - ((6 \times (4 - 8)) + 5))}{((3 \times (2 + 9)) + (7 - 0))} &:= \frac{(1 - ((6 \times 4) - (8 \times 5)))}{(32 + (9 - (7 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 - (6 - ((4 \times 8) - 5)))}{(3 - (29 - 70))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (6 - (4 \times (8 + 5))))}{((3 \times 29) + (7 - 0))} &:= \frac{(1 - (6 - (4 + (8 - 5))))}{((3 \times 2) - (9 - (7 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 - (6 - (48 + 5)))}{(3 \times (2 \times (9 + (7 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (6 + (4 - (8 \times 5))))}{(3 - (2 + (9 - 70)))} &:= \frac{(1 - (6 + (4 - (8 + 5))))}{(((3 - 2)^9) + (7 - 0))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (((6 - 4)^8) + 5))}{(3 + ((2^9) + (7 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times ((6 \times 4) + (8 + 5)))}{(((3^2) \times 9) - (7 - 0))} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((6 \times 4) + 85))}{((32 \times 9) - 70)} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((6 + (4 - 8))^5)}{(3 - (2 - (9 \times (7 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (6 - ((4 - 8) \times 5)))}{(3 - ((2 - 9) \times (7 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (6 - (4 - (8 + 5))))}{(32 - (9 - (7 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (6 - (4 - (8 - 5))))}{((3 + 2) \times (9 - (7 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (6 \times (4 \times (8 - 5))))}{((3^2) \times (9 + (7 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (6 \times (4 + (8 - 5))))}{(3 + (2 + (9 + 70)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (6 \times (48 + 5)))}{((3 \times 2) + (9 \times 70))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (6 \times 485))}{(3 \times (2 \times 970))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (6^{4-8+5}))}{(3 \times (2^{9-7+0}))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (6 + (4 \times (8 - 5))))}{((3 \times 2)^{9-7+0})} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (6 + (4 + (8 - 5))))}{((3 \times (2 + 9)) - (7 - 0))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (6 + (48 - 5)))}{(3 - (2 - (97 - 0)))} &:= \frac{1^{6485}}{((3 - 2) \times (9 - (7 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (((6 \times 4) + 8) \times 5))}{(329 - (7 - 0))} &:= \frac{(1 + ((6 + (4 - 8)) \times 5))}{((3 \times 2) + (9 + (7 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 + ((6 + (4 - 8))^5)}{(3 + (2 - (9 - 70)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + ((6 - 4)^{8-5}))}{((3^2) \times (9 - (7 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (6 - ((4 - 8) \times 5)))}{(3 \times (2 + (9 + (7 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(1 + (6 \times (4 + (8 + 5))))}{(3 + (29 \times (7 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (6^{4-8+5}))}{(3 + ((2 \times 9) - (7 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (6 + ((4 \times 8) + 5)))}{((3^2) + (9 + 70))} &:= \frac{(1 + (6 + ((4 \times 8) - 5)))}{(3 + (2 + (9 \times (7 - 0))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (6 + (4 - (8 - 5))))}{(32 - (9 + (7 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (6 + (4 \times (8 - 5))))}{(((3 + 2) \times 9) - (7 - 0))} &:= \frac{(1 + (6 + (4 + (8 \times 5))))}{(3 + (2 + (97 - 0)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (6 + (4 + (8 + 5))))}{(32 + (9 + (7 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (6 + (4 + (8 - 5))))}{(3 + ((2 \times 9) + (7 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (64 - (8 - 5)))}{((3 \times (2 \times 9)) + 70)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (64 + 85))}{(3 + (297 - 0))} &:= \frac{(16 - ((4 - 8) \times 5))}{((3^2) + (9 \times (7 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(16 \times (4 + (8 - 5)))}{((3 + 29) \times (7 - 0))} \\ &:= \frac{(16 + ((4 \times 8) + 5))}{((3^2) + (97 - 0))} &:= \frac{(16 + (48 \times 5))}{(32 \times (9 + (7 - 0)))} &:= \frac{16 + 485}{32 + 970} \end{aligned}$$

► **18645**
37290

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(((1 - (8 - (6 + 4)))^5)}{(3 \times (72 + 90))} &:= \frac{((1^{86}) \times (4 + 5))}{((3 \times (7 + 2)) - (9 - 0))} &:= \frac{((1^8) \times (6 \times (4 + 5)))}{(3 \times (7 + (29 - 0)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((1^8) \times (6 + (4 \times 5)))}{(3 - (7 \times (2 - (9 - 0))))} := \frac{((1 + ((8 \times 6) - 4)) \times 5)}{(((3 \times 7)^2) + (9 - 0))} := \frac{((1 + (8 + (6 + 4))) \times 5)}{(3 + (7 + (2 \times 90)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (8 + (6 - 4))) \times 5)}{((3 + 7) \times (2 + (9 - 0)))} := \frac{((1 + (8 + 6)) \times 45)}{(3 \times ((7 - 2) \times 90))} := \frac{((1 + (8 - 6))^{4+5})}{((3^7) \times (2 \times (9 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + 8) \times (6 + (4 \times 5)))}{((3 + (7^2)) \times (9 - 0))} := \frac{((18 \times 6) + (4 + 5))}{((3^{7-2}) - (9 - 0))} := \frac{((18 + 6) \times (4 + 5))}{(((3 \times 7)^2) - (9 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{((18 - 6) \times 45)}{((3 + (7 + 2)) \times 90)} := \frac{(1 - (8 - (6 + 45)))}{(3 - (7 - (2 + 90)))} := \frac{(1 - (8 \times (6 - (4 + 5))))}{((3 \times 7) + (29 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (8 \times (6 \times (4 - 5))))}{(3 + (7 - (2 - 90)))} := \frac{(1 - (8 + (6 - (4 \times 5))))}{(3 - (7 - (2 \times (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 \times ((8 \times (6 - 4)) + 5))}{(3 \times (7 - (2 - (9 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((8^{6-4}) + 5))}{((3 \times (7^2)) - (9 - 0))} := \frac{(1 \times ((8 + (6 + 4)) \times 5))}{((3 + 7) \times (2 \times (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 \times ((8 + 6) \times (4 + 5)))}{((3^{7-2}) + (9 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((8 + 64) \times 5))}{((3 + (7 - 2)) \times 90)} := \frac{(1 \times ((86 + 4) \times 5))}{(((3 + 7)^2) \times (9 - 0))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 - (6 - (4 \times 5))))}{(3 - ((7^2) - 90))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 - (6 + (4 - 5))))}{((3 \times (7 - 2)) - (9 - 0))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (6 + (4 - 5))))}{(3 + (7 \times (2 + (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (64 \times 5)))}{((3 + 7) \times (2^9 + 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 + ((6 \times 4) - 5)))}{(3 \times (7 + (2 + (9 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 + ((6 - 4) \times 5))}{((3 \times (7 + 2)) + (9 - 0))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 + (6 - (4 + 5))))}{(((3 + 7)^2) - 90)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 + (6 - (4 - 5))))}{(37 + (2 - (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 + ((7 \times 2) + (9 - 0)))}{(1 + (((8 \times 6) + 4) \times 5))} := \frac{(3 \times (7 \times 2)) + 90}{(1 + ((8 + (6 - 4)) \times 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (86 - (4 - 5)))}{(3 \times ((7^2) + (9 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 + (7 + (2^9 + 0)))}{(1 + (8 - (6 + (4 - 5))))} := \frac{(3 + (7 + (2 + 90)))}{(1 + (8 \times ((6 \times 4) - 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (7 - 2)) + (9 - 0))}{(1 + (8 \times (6 + (4 - 5))))} := \frac{(3 + ((7 \times 2) - (9 - 0)))}{(1 + (8 + (6 - (4 - 5))))} := \frac{(3 \times 72) + 90}{(1 + (8 + (6 \times (4 + 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((3 - 7) \times 2) + 90)}{(1 + (8 + (6 + (4 + 5))))} := \frac{((3 \times 7) + (2 + (9 - 0)))}{(1 + (8 + (6 + (4 - 5))))} := \frac{(3 \times 72) - 90}{(1 + (8 + (6 + 45)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + ((7 - 2) \times (9 - 0)))}{(1 + (8 + (64 + 5)))} := \frac{(3 + (7 + (2 \times (9 - 0))))}{(1 + (86 - (4 - 5)))} := \frac{(3 \times (7^2) - (9 - 0))}{(1 + (86 - 45))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (7^2)) + (9 - 0))}{(18 \times ((6 + 4) \times 5))} := \frac{(3 - (7 - (2 \times 90)))}{(18 \times (6 \times (4 + 5)))} := \frac{(3 - (7 + (2 - 90)))}{(18 + (6 + (4 + 5)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 + 7) \times (2 \times 90))}{(186 \times (4 + 5))} := \frac{(3 \times (72 \times (9 - 0)))}{186 + 45} := \frac{(3 + (72 - (9 - 0)))}{186 - 45} \\
 &:= \frac{(372 \times (9 - 0))}{372 + 90} := \frac{372 + 90}{372 - 90}
 \end{aligned}$$

► 29067
58134

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((2 \times (9 - 0)) - 6) \times 7)}{((5 + (8 + 1)) \times (3 \times 4))} := \frac{((2 \times (9 - (0 \times 6))) + 7)}{(5 \times (8 + (1 - (3 - 4))))} := \frac{((2 \times (9 - (0 - 6))) + 7)}{(5 + (81 - (3 \times 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (9 - (0 - 6))) - 7)}{(5 + (8 - (1 - 34)))} := \frac{((2 \times (9 \times (0 \times 6))) + 7)}{(5 + (8 - (1 \times (3 - 4))))} := \frac{((2 \times (9 + (0 - 6))) + 7)}{(5 + (8 + (1 + (3 \times 4))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (9 - 0)) - (6 + 7))}{((5 \times (8 + (1 - (3 + 4))))} := \frac{((2 \times (9 - 0)) - (6 - 7))}{(((5 + (8 + 1)) \times 3) - 4)} := \frac{((2 \times (9 - 0)) + (6 + 7))}{(58 + ((1^3) \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (9 - 0)) + (6 - 7))}{((5 \times (8 + (1 - 3))) + 4)} := \frac{((2 \times (9 - 0)) + 67)}{((2 \times (90 + 6)) + 7)} := \frac{((2 \times (90 + 6)) + 7)}{((5 \times 81) - (3 + 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (90 + 6)) - 7)}{(5 \times (81 - (3 + 4)))} := \frac{((2 \times 90) + (6 + 7))}{((5 \times (81 - 3)) - 4)} := \frac{((2^{9-06}) + 7)}{(5 - (8 + (1 - 34)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^{9-06}) - 7)}{(5 + (8 + (1 - (3 \times 4))))} := \frac{((2 - 9) \times (0 - (6 \times 7)))}{(581 + (3 + 4))} := \frac{((2 - 90) \times (6 - 7))}{(((5 \times 8) + (1 + 3)) \times 4)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(2 - ((9 \times (0 \times 6)) - 7))}{(5 + (8 + ((1^3) + 4)))} := \frac{(2 - ((9 \times (0 - 6)) + 7))}{(5 + (81 + (3 \times 4)))} := \frac{(2 - ((9 \times (0 - 6)) - 7))}{((5 \times (8 + 1)) + (3^4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (9 \times (0 \times 67)))}{(5 - (8 - (1 \times (3 + 4))))} := \frac{(2 - (9 + (0 - (6 \times 7))))}{(5 \times (8 - (1 - (3 + 4))))} := \frac{(2 - (9 + (0 - (6 + 7))))}{(5 + (8 + (1 \times (3 - 4))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (9 + (0 - 67)))}{(5 \times ((8 + (1 - 3)) \times 4))} := \frac{(2 \times ((9 - (0 - 6)) \times 7))}{(5 \times ((8 + 13) \times 4))} := \frac{(2 \times ((9 \times (0 \times 6)) + 7))}{((5 \times (8 \times 1)) - (3 \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((9 \times (0 + 6)) + 7))}{(5 + ((81 \times 3) - 4))} := \frac{(2 \times ((9 + (0 - 6)) \times 7))}{((5 - (8 \times (1 - 3))) \times 4)} := \frac{(2 \times (9 - ((0 \times 6) - 7)))}{((5 \times (8 + (1 + 3))) + 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (9 - (0 - (6 - 7))))}{(5 - (8 - (1 + 34)))} := \frac{(2 \times (9 - (0 \times 67)))}{((5 \times (8 \times (1^3))) - 4)} := \frac{(5 + ((81 \times 3) + 4))}{(2 \times (90 - (6 \times 7)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (9 \times (0 + (6 + 7))))}{((5 \times 8) - 1) \times (3 \times 4)} := \frac{(2 \times (9 + (0 - (6 - 7))))}{(5 \times (8 - (1 + (3 - 4))))} := \frac{((5 \times (8 + 1)) + 3) \times 4}{(2 \times (90 - 67))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (90 + (6 + 7)))}{((5 \times 81) + (3 + 4))} := \frac{(2 \times (90 + (6 - 7)))}{((5 + (81 + 3)) \times 4)} := \frac{(58 + (1 \times 34))}{2^{9+0 \times 6-7}} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 - (8 + (1 - (3 \times 4))))}{(2 + (9 - (0 \times 67)))} := \frac{(5 + (8 + (1 + 34)))}{(2 + (9 - (0 - 67)))} := \frac{(5 + (8 + (1 \times (3 + 4))))}{(2 + (9 + (0 - (6 - 7))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (8 + (13 - 4)))}{(2 + (90 - (6 \times 7)))} := \frac{((5 \times (8 \times (1 + 3))) - 4)}{(2 + (90 + (6 + 7)))} := \frac{(5 + (8 - (1 - (3 \times 4))))}{(29 - (0 - (6 - 7)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times (8 + (1 \times (3 \times 4))))}{(29 - (0 \times 67))} := \frac{(5 \times (8 + (1 \times 34)))}{(29 \times ((0 \times 6) + 7))} := \frac{((5 + (8 + (1^3))) \times 4)}{(29 \times (0 + (6 + 7)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(58 - (1 + (3 - 4)))}{(29 + ((0 \times 6) - 7))} := \frac{((5 \times 81) - (3 - 4))}{(29 + (0 - (6 - 7)))} := \frac{(58 \times (1 + (3 \times 4)))}{(290 - (6 - 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 \times (8 \times (1^3))) + 4)}{((5 \times (8 \times ((1^3) \times 4)))} := \frac{(581 - (3 - 4))}{(581 - (3 - 4))}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.53 55 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13485}{26970} &:= \frac{(((1 + 3) \times 4) + (8 - 5))}{(2 + (6^{9-7+0}))} := \frac{((1 - (3 + (4 - 8)))^5)}{(2 + (69 - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{((1 - (3 - 4)) \times (8 + 5))}{(26 \times (9 - (7 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{1^{348} + 5}{(2 - (6 - (9 + (7 - 0))))} := \frac{((1^3) \times (4 + (8 + 5)))}{(((2 - 6) \times 9) + 70)} := \frac{((1^3) \times (4 + 85))}{((2 \times (6 \times 9)) + 70)} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (3^4)) \times 85)}{(2 \times 6970)} := \frac{((1 + (3 + 4)) \times (8 + 5))}{((2 \times 69) + 70)} := \frac{((1 + (3 + 4))^{8-5})}{((2^6) \times (9 + (7 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + 3) \times (4 \times (8 + 5)))}{(26 \times (9 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{((1 + 34) \times (8 - 5))}{(2 \times ((6 + 9) \times (7 - 0)))} := \frac{((1 - 3) \times (4 - (8 \times 5)))}{((2 \times 6)^{9-7+0})} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - ((3 \times (4 - 8)) + 5))}{2^{6-9+7+0}} := \frac{(1 - ((3 - 4) \times (8 + 5)))}{(26 + (9 - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 - (3 - (4 \times (8 + 5))))}{((2 \times (6 + 9)) + 70)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (3 - (4 \times 85)))}{(26^{9-7+0})} := \frac{(1 - (3 - (4^{8-5})))}{(2 \times (69 - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 - (3 - (48 \times 5)))}{(2 + (6 \times (9 + 70)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (3 \times ((4 - 8) \times 5)))}{(2 \times ((6 \times 9) + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 - (3 + (4 - (8 \times 5))))}{((2 \times 69) - 70)} := \frac{(1 - (3 + (4 - (8 + 5))))}{(2 + (6 \times (9 - (7 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (3 - 485))}{(2 - (6 - 970))} := \frac{(1 \times ((3 \times (4 + 8)) - 5))}{((2^6) - (9 - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 \times ((3 \times 4) - (8 - 5)))}{(2 - ((6 \times 9) - 70))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((3 \times 48) - 5))}{(2 \times (69 + 70))} := \frac{(1 \times ((3 + (4 \times 8)) \times 5))}{((2 - (6 - 9)) \times 70)} := \frac{(1 \times ((3 + 4) \times 85))}{((2 + (6 + 9)) \times 70)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (3 - (4 - (8 \times 5))))}{(2 + (69 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 \times (3 - (4 - (8 + 5))))}{(2 \times (6 \times (9 - (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 \times (3 \times (4 \times (8 - 5))))}{(2 \times (6^{9-7+0}))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (3 \times (4 + (8 - 5))))}{(26 + (9 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 \times (3^{4-8+5}))}{(2 + (6 - (9 - (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 \times (3 + ((4 + 8) \times 5))}{(2 + ((6 \times 9) + 70))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (3 + (4^{8-5})))}{(2 \times (6 - (9 - 70)))} := \frac{(1 \times (3 + (4 + (8 \times 5))))}{(2 \times ((6 \times 9) - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{1^{3485}}{(2 + 6) \times 9 - 70} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + ((3^4) - (8 + 5)))}{(2 \times (6 + (9 \times (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 + ((3^4) + (8 \times 5)))}{((2 - 6) \times (9 - 70))} := \frac{(1 + ((3 + (4 + 8)) \times 5))}{(2 \times (69 + (7 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + ((34 - 8) \times 5))}{(269 - (7 - 0))} := \frac{(1 + (3 - ((4 - 8) \times 5)))}{((2^6) - (9 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + (3 - (4 - (8 \times 5))))}{(2 \times (69 + (7 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (3 - (4 - 85)))}{(2 \times (6 + (9 + 70)))} := \frac{(1 + (3 \times ((4 \times 8) - 5)))}{((26 \times 9) - 70)} := \frac{(1 + (3 \times (4 + (8 - 5))))}{(2 \times (6 + (9 + (7 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (3^{4-8+5}))}{(2 \times (6 - (9 - (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 + (3 + ((4 + 8) \times 5))}{((2^6) \times (9 - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + (3 + (4 - (8 - 5))))}{(2 + (6 + (9 - (7 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (3 + 485))}{(2 + (6 + 970))} := \frac{(1 + (34 \times (8 - 5)))}{(2 \times (6 + (97 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 + 3485)}{(2 + 6970)} \\
 &:= \frac{(13 - ((4 - 8) \times 5))}{((2^6) + (9 - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(13 - (4 - (8 \times 5)))}{(2 + (6 \times (9 + (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(13 + (48 \times 5))}{((2^6) \times 9) - 70} \\
 &:= \frac{(13 + 485)}{(26 + 970)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► **26709**
53418

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((2 \times 6) - (7 - 0)) \times 9)}{(((5 - 3) \times 41) + 8)} := \frac{(((2^6) - (7 - 0)) \times 9)}{((53 + 4) \times 18)} := \frac{(((2 + 6) \times (7 - 0)) + 9)}{(5 \times (34 - (1 \times 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((2 + 6) \times (7 - 0)) - 9)}{(5 + ((3^4 \times 1) + 8))} := \frac{((2 - (6 - (7 - 0))) \times 9)}{((5 - (3 - 4)) \times (1 + 8))} := \frac{((2 - (6 + 7)) \times (0 - 9))}{(((5 \times 3) - 4) \times 18)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (6 - (7 - 0))) + 9)}{(5 + (3 \times (4 - (1^8))))} := \frac{((2 \times (6 + (7 - 0))) + 9)}{(5 \times (3 + (4 - (1 - 8))))} := \frac{((2 \times (6 + (7 - 0))) - 9)}{(5 - (3 - (4 \times (1 \times 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times 6) - (7 - (0 \times 9)))}{(5 + ((3 \times 4) + (1 - 8)))} := \frac{((2^6) - (7 - (0 - 9)))}{((5 + (3 + (4 \times 1))) \times 8)} := \frac{((2^6) + (7 - (0 - 9)))}{((5 + (3 \times (4 + 1))) \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + (6 - (7 - 0))) \times 9)}{(5 + ((3 \times 4) + (1^8)))} := \frac{((2 + 6) \times (7 - (0 \times 9)))}{((5 + (3 \times (4 - 1))) \times 8)} := \frac{((2 + 6) \times (7 - (0 - 9)))}{((5 + (3^{4-1})) \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + 6) \times (70 - 9))}{(((5^3) - (4 - 1)) \times 8)} := \frac{((26 - (7 - 0)) \times 9)}{(((5 \times 3) + 4) \times 18)} := \frac{((2 - 6) \times (7 \times (0 - 9)))}{(((5 + 3)^{4-1}) - 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - ((6 - (7 - 0)) \times 9))}{(5 + (3 - (4 - 18)))} := \frac{(2 - (6 - (7 - (0 \times 9))))}{(5 - (3 - (4 \times (1^8))))} := \frac{(2 - (6 - (7 - (0 - 9))))}{(5 - (3 - (4 + 18)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (6 - (70 + 9)))}{(5 \times ((3 \times 4) + 18))} := \frac{(2 - (6 - (70 - 9)))}{(((5^3) - (4 - (1 - 8))))} := \frac{(2 - (6 \times (7 \times (0 \times 9))))}{(5 + (3 - (4 \times (1^8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (6 \times (7 + (0 - 9))))}{(5 + ((3 \times (4 + 1)) + 8))} := \frac{(2 \times ((6 \times (7 - 0)) + 9))}{((53 \times (4 \times 1)) - 8)} := \frac{(2 \times ((6^7 + 0) \times 9))}{((5 - (3 - 4)) \times (1 + 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((6 - 7) \times (0 - 9)))}{(5 + (3 - (4 \times (1 - 8))))} := \frac{(2 \times (6 - (7 + (0 - 9))))}{(5 + (3^{4-1^8}))} := \frac{(2 \times (6 \times (7 - (0 - 9))))}{((53 - (4 + 1)) \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (6 + (7 - (0 \times 9))))}{(((5 \times (3 \times (4 \times 1))) - 8)} := \frac{(2 \times (6 + (7 - (0 - 9))))}{((5 + (3 + (4 - 1))) \times 8)} := \frac{(2 \times (6 + (7 + (0 - 9))))}{(5 - (3 + (4 - 18)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (67 - (0 - 9)))}{((5 + (34 - 1)) \times 8)} := \frac{2^{(-6+7) \times 09}}{(5 + (3 \times 41)) \times 8} := \frac{2^6 + 7 \times 0 \times 9}{((5 + ((3 \times 4) - 1)) \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{2^{6-7+09}}{((5 + 3)^{4-1^8})} := \frac{(2 + (6 - (7 - (0 \times 9))))}{((5 \times (3 - 4)) - (1 - 8))} := \frac{(2 + (6 - (7 + (0 - 9))))}{(5 + (3 \times (4 + (1^8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (6 + (7 - (0 \times 9))))}{(5 + (3 + (4 + 18)))} := \frac{(2 + (6 + (7 - (0 - 9))))}{((5 - (3 - (4 \times 1))) \times 8)} := \frac{(2 + (6 + (7 + (0 - 9))))}{(5 + (3 + (4 \times (1^8))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(2 + (6 + (70 + 9)))}{((5^3) + (41 + 8))} & := \frac{(2 + (6 + (70 - 9)))}{((5^3) + (4 + (1 + 8)))} & := \frac{(2 + (67 + (0 - 9)))}{(5 + ((3 \times 41) - 8))} \\
 & \frac{(26 - (7 - (0 \times 9)))}{(5 + (3 \times (4 - (1 - 8))))} & \frac{(26 - (7 \times (0 - 9)))}{((5 \times (34 \times 1)) + 8)} & \frac{(26 - (7 + (0 - 9)))}{((5 - (3 - (4 + 1))) \times 8)} \\
 & \frac{(26 \times (70 \times 9))}{(((5 + 3)^{4+1}) - 8)} & \frac{(26 + (7 - (0 \times 9)))}{(26 + (70 + 9))} & \frac{(26 + (70 + 9))}{(5 \times (34 + (1 \times 8)))} \\
 & \frac{((5 + 3)^{4+1} - 8)}{(267 - (0 \times 9))} & \frac{(53 + (4 + (1 + 8)))}{(267 - (0 - 9))} & \frac{(5 \times (34 + (1 \times 8)))}{(267 \times (0 + 9))} \\
 & \frac{(267 - (0 \times 9))}{(534 \times (1^8))} & \frac{(267 - (0 - 9))}{(534 + 18)} & \frac{(267 \times (0 + 9))}{(534 \times (1 + 8))} \\
 & \frac{(534 \times (1^8))}{(267 + (0 - 9))} & & \\
 & \frac{(267 + (0 - 9))}{(534 - 18)} & &
 \end{aligned}$$

3.54 56 Equivalent Blocks

► $\frac{10942}{87536}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(((1 + 09) \times 4) + 2)}{(8 \times (((7 + 5) \times 3) + 6))} & := \frac{(((10 + 9) \times 4) + 2)}{(8 \times (75 - (3 - 6)))} & := \frac{(((1 - (0 - (9 \times 4))) \times 2)}{(8 \times 7) + 536)} \\
 & \frac{(((1 - (0 - (9 + 4))) \times 2)}{(8 \times (7 + ((5 \times 3) + 6)))} & \frac{(((1 - (0 - (9 - 4)))^2)}{(8 \times ((7 - 5) \times (3 \times 6)))} & \frac{(((1 + 09) \times (4 + 2))}{((8 + (75 - 3)) \times 6)} \\
 & \frac{((1 + 09) \times (4 - 2))}{(8 \times (7 - (5 - (3 \times 6))))} & \frac{((1 + 09)^{4-2})}{(8 + ((7 + (5^3)) \times 6))} & \frac{((1^{09}) \times (4 + 2))}{(8 - (7 - (53 - 6)))} \\
 & \frac{((1^{09}) + (4 \times 2))}{(8 \times (7 + (5 + (3 - 6))))} & \frac{((1^{09}) + 42)}{(8 \times ((7^5-3) - 6))} & \frac{((10 \times (9 + 4)) + 2)}{(8 \times ((7 + (5 \times 3)) \times 6))} \\
 & \frac{((10 \times (9 - 4)) - 2)}{(8 \times (7 + (5 + 36)))} & \frac{((10 \times 9) - (4 + 2))}{(8 \times (7 \times ((5 - 3) \times 6)))} & \frac{((10 \times 9) + (4 \times 2))}{(8 \times (7 \times (5 + (3 + 6))))} \\
 & \frac{((10^9)^{4-2})}{((8^7) \times ((5^3)^6))} & \frac{((10 + (9 + 4)) \times 2)}{(8 + ((7 + 53) \times 6))} & \frac{(1 - (0 - ((9 \times 4)^2)))}{(8 + (((7 + 5)^3) \times 6))} \\
 & \frac{(1 - (0 - ((9 \times 4) + 2)))}{(8 \times (75 - 36))} & \frac{(1 - (0 - ((9 + 4) \times 2)))}{((8 - (7 - 5)) \times 36)} & \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 - (4 \times 2))))}{(8 - (7 + (5 \times (3 - 6))))} \\
 & \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 - (4 + 2))))}{(8 - (7 + (5 - 36)))} & \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 \times (4 + 2))))}{(8 \times ((7^5-3) + 6))} & \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 \times (4 - 2))))}{(8 \times (7 + ((5 - 3) \times 6)))} \\
 & \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 + (4^2))))}{(8 \times ((7 \times 5) - (3 + 6)))} & \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 + (4 + 2))))}{(8 \times (7 + ((5 \times 3) - 6)))} & \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 + (4 - 2))))}{((8 - (7 - (5 \times 3))) \times 6)} \\
 & \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 + 42)))}{(8 \times (7 + (5 \times (3 + 6))))} & \frac{(1 - (0 - (94 + 2)))}{(8 \times (7 + (5 \times (3 \times 6))))} & \frac{(1 - (0 - (94 - 2)))}{(8 \times (75 + (3 \times 6)))} \\
 & \frac{(1 - (0 \times (9 - 42)))}{(8 - (((7 - 5) \times 3) - 6))} & \frac{(1 - (0 - 942))}{(8 + 7536)} & \frac{(1 \times (0 - (9 - (4^2))))}{(8 + (7 + (5 + 36)))} \\
 & \frac{(1 \times (0 - (9 - 42)))}{((8 + ((7 + 5) \times 3)) \times 6)} & \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((9 \times 4) + 2)))}{(8 \times (7 - (5 - 36)))} & \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((9 - 4) \times 2)))}{(8 + (75 + (3 - 6)))} \\
 & \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 - (4 + 2))))}{(8 \times (7 + (5 - (3 + 6))))} & \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 \times (4 \times 2))))}{(8 \times (75 + (3 - 6)))} & \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 \times (4^2))))}{((8^7-5) \times (3 \times 6))} \\
 & \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 \times (4 + 2))))}{(8 \times (7 + (53 - 6)))} & \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 \times (4 - 2))))}{(8 \times ((7 - 5) \times (3 + 6)))} & \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9^{4+2})))}{(8 \times ((7 + (5 - 3))^6))} \\
 & \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 + (4 \times 2))))}{(8 \times ((7 \times 5) - (3 \times 6)))} & \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 + (4^2))))}{(8 + (((7 \times 5) - 3) \times 6))} & \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 + (4 + 2))))}{(8 \times (7 + (5 - (3 - 6))))} \\
 & \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 + (4 - 2))))}{(8 \times (7 - (5 - (3 + 6))))} & \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 + 42)))}{((8 + (7 + 53)) \times 6)} & \frac{(1 + (0 - (9 - (4^2))))}{(8 + (7 \times (5 - (3 - 6))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(10 \times (9 - (4 + 2)))}{(8 \times (7 + (5 + (3 \times 6))))} := \frac{(10 + ((9 \times 4) - 2))}{(8 \times ((7 \times 5) + (3 + 6)))} := \frac{(10 + (9 - (4 + 2)))}{((8 \times 7) + ((5 + 3) \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 + (9 \times (4 + 2)))}{8^{7+5-3-6}} := \frac{(10 + (9 + (4 - 2)))}{(8 \times (7 + (5 + (3 + 6))))} := \frac{(109 \times (4 + 2))}{((875 - 3) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(109 + (4 - 2))}{(8 \times ((7 \times (5 \times 3)) + 6))} := \frac{(109 - 42)}{((8 - 7) \times 536)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► **18546**
37092

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((1 - (8 - (5 + 4)))^6)}{((3 + (70 - 9)) \times 2)} := \frac{((1^{85}) \times 46)}{(((3 + (7 - 0)) \times 9) + 2)} := \frac{((1^8) \times ((5 \times 4) + 6))}{(3 - (7 \times (0 - (9 - 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (8 \times (5 \times 4))) \times 6)}{(3 \times (7 \times (0 + 92)))} := \frac{((1 + (8 - 5)) \times 46)}{((3 - 7) \times (0 - 92))} := \frac{((1 + 8) \times (5 \times (4 + 6)))}{(((3 \times (7 - 0)) + 9)^2)} \\
 &:= \frac{((18 + (5 + 4)) \times 6)}{((3 - 7) \times (0 - (9^2)))} := \frac{((18 + (5 - 4)) \times 6)}{((3 \times 70) + (9 \times 2))} := \frac{((18 + 5) \times 46)}{((18 + 5) \times 46)} \\
 &:= \frac{((185 + 4) \times 6)}{((3^7 + 0) + (9^2))} := \frac{(1 - (8 - (5 + (4 \times 6))))}{(37 - (0 - (9 - 2)))} := \frac{(1 - (8 - (5 + 46)))}{(37 - (0 - 9))^2} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (8 + (5 \times (4 - 6))))}{(3 \times ((7 \times (0 \times 9)) + 2))} := \frac{(1 - (8 + (5 - 46)))}{(3 - ((7 \times (0 - 9)) - 2))} := \frac{(3 - (7 + (0 - 92)))}{(1 - (8 - (5 + 46)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((8 \times (5 + 4)) + 6))}{(3 \times (70 - (9 \times 2)))} := \frac{(1 \times ((8 \times (5 + 4)) - 6))}{((3 - (7 \times (0 - 9))) \times 2)} := \frac{(1 \times ((8 - 5) \times (4 \times 6)))}{(3 - (7 + (0 - 92)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((8 - 5) \times (4 + 6)))}{(((3 \times (7 - 0)) + 9) \times 2)} := \frac{(1 \times (8 - ((5 - 4)^6))}{(3 - (7 + (0 - (9 \times 2))))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 - (5 - (4 \times 6))))}{(3 \times (7 - (0 - (9 + 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 - (5 - (4 + 6))))}{(37 + (0 - (9 + 2)))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 - (5 + (4 - 6))))}{(3 + (7 - (0 \times 92)))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 \times ((5 - 4) \times 6)))}{(3 \times ((7 - (0 - 9)) \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (5 + (4 - 6))))}{(37 - (0 - (9 + 2)))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 \times (54 - 6)))}{(3 \times ((7 - (0 - 9))^2))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 + (5 - (4 - 6))))}{(1 \times (8 - (5 - (4 \times 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (8 + (5 + (4 \times 6))))}{(37 \times ((0 \times 9) + 2))} := \frac{(1 \times (8 + (5 + (4 + 6))))}{((3 \times (7 - (0 - 9))) - 2)} := \frac{(1 \times (8 + (5 + 46)))}{(37 + (0 - (9 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{1^{8546}}{(3 + (7 + (0 - 9))) \times 2} := \frac{(1 + ((8 \times 5) - (4 \times 6)))}{(((3 - 7) \times (0 - 9)) - 2)} := \frac{(1 + ((8 \times 5) + (4 + 6)))}{(3 + (7 - (0 - 92)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + ((8 + (5 - 4)) \times 6))}{((3 + (7 - 0)) \times (9 + 2))} := \frac{(1 + ((8 - 5) \times (4 + 6)))}{(3 + (70 - (9 + 2)))} := \frac{(1 + ((8 - 5) \times 46))}{(370 - 92)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (8 - (5 - (4 \times 6))))}{((37 + (0 - 9)) \times 2)} := \frac{(1 + (8 - (5 - (4 + 6))))}{(3 + (7 - (0 - (9 \times 2))))} := \frac{(1 + (8 - (5 \times (4 - 6))))}{((3 + (7 - (0 - 9))) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (8 - (5 + (4 - 6))))}{(3 + (7 - ((0 \times 9) - 2)))} := \frac{(1 + (8 - (5 - 46)))}{((3 + (7 - (0 \times 9)))^2)} := \frac{(1 + (8 \times (5 + (4 - 6))))}{(1 + (8 - (5 + 46)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (8 + ((5 \times 4) + 6)))}{((3 + (7 - 0)) \times (9 - 2))} := \frac{(1 + (8 + ((5 - 4)^6))}{((3 + (7 - (0 \times 9))) \times 2)} := \frac{(1 + (8 + (5 - (4 + 6))))}{(3 + (7 + ((0 \times 9) - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (8 + (5 - (4 - 6))))}{((3 \times (7 - 0)) + (9 + 2))} := \frac{(1 + (8 + (5 + (4 - 6))))}{(((3 \times (7 - 0)) - 9) \times 2)} := \frac{(1 + (8 + (54 \times 6)))}{(37 \times (0 + (9 \times 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (85 + (4 + 6)))}{((3 \times 70) - (9 \times 2))} := \frac{(1 + (85 + 46))}{(3 \times (7 - (0 - (9^2))))} := \frac{(1 + (85 - 46))}{(3 - (7 \times (0 - (9 + 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(18 + ((5 \times 4) - 6))}{(3 - ((7 \times (0 - 9)) + 2))} := \frac{(18 + (5 + (4 + 6)))}{(3 + (70 - (9 - 2)))} := \frac{(18 + (5 + (4 - 6)))}{(3 \times (7 - (0 - (9 - 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(185 + (4 - 6))}{(3 \times ((70 - 9) \times 2))} := \frac{185 + 46}{370 + 92}
 \end{aligned}$$

► **21735**
86940

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((2 \times (1 + 7)) + 3) \times 5)}{((86 + 9) \times (4 - 0))} := \frac{(((2 + 17) \times 3) + 5)}{((8 + (6 \times 9)) \times (4 - 0))} := \frac{((2 - (1^{73})) \times 5)}{(8 - ((6 - 9) \times (4 - 0)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (1 + (7 \times 3))) - 5)}{(((8 \times 6) - 9) \times (4 - 0))} := \frac{((2 \times (1 + 73)) - 5)}{(8 + (6 \times (94 - 0)))} := \frac{((2^{1 \times 7}) + (3 - 5))}{((8 + 6) \times (9 \times (4 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + ((1 + 7) \times 3)) \times 5)}{(8 \times (69 - (4 - 0)))} := \frac{((2 + (1 \times (7 + 3))) \times 5)}{(8 \times (6 \times (9 - (4 - 0))))} := \frac{((2 + (1 + (7 \times 3))) \times 5)}{(8 \times ((6 + 9) \times (4 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + 17) \times (3 + 5))}{(8 + ((6 + 9) \times 40))} := \frac{((2 - 1) \times (7 \times (3 + 5)))}{(8 + (6 \times (9 \times (4 - 0))))} := \frac{((21 \times 7) - (3 + 5))}{((8 \times 69) + (4 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{((21 \times 7) + (3^5))}{(((8 \times 6) - 9) \times 40)} := \frac{((21 + 73) \times 5)}{((8 - 6) \times 940)} := \frac{(2 - ((1 - (7 + 3)) \times 5))}{((8 - 6) \times (94 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (1 - ((7 - 3) \times 5)))}{(((8 \times 6) + (9 \times (4 - 0)))} := \frac{(2 - (1 - (7 \times (3 + 5))))}{(((8 \times 6) + 9) \times (4 - 0))} := \frac{(2 - (1 - (7 + (3 \times 5))))}{((8 + (6 + 9)) \times (4 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (1 + (7 - 35)))}{((8 \times (6 + 9)) - (4 - 0))} := \frac{(2 \times (((1 + 7)^3) \times 5))}{(((8 - 6)^9) \times 40)} := \frac{(2 \times ((1 + (7 + 3)) \times 5))}{(8 \times (6 + (9 + 40)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((1 + (7 - 3)) \times 5))}{((8 + (6 - 9)) \times 40)} := \frac{(2 \times ((1 + 7) \times (3 + 5)))}{((8 \times 69) - 40)} := \frac{(2 \times ((17 + 3) \times 5))}{(8 \times (6 + (94 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (1 - (7 - 35)))}{(8 \times (69 - 40))} := \frac{(2 \times (1 \times ((7 + 3) \times 5)))}{(8 \times ((6 \times 9) - (4 - 0)))} := \frac{(2 \times (1 \times ((7 - 3) \times 5)))}{(8 \times (6 + (94 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (1 \times (7 - (3 - 5))))}{((8 - 6) \times (9 \times (4 - 0)))} := \frac{(2 \times (1 \times (7 + 35)))}{(8 \times (6 + (9 \times (4 - 0))))} := \frac{(2 \times (1 \times (73 + 5)))}{(8 \times (6 \times (9 + (4 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (1 + ((7 + 3) \times 5)))}{((8 \times 6) + (9 \times 40))} := \frac{(2 \times (1 + (7 - (3 - 5))))}{((8 \times (6 + 9)) - 40)} := \frac{(2 \times (1 + (73 \times 5)))}{(8 \times (6 + (9 \times 40)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((8 - 6)^9) + 40)}{(2 \times (1 \times (7 - (3 - 5))))} := \frac{(8 \times (6 + (9 + (4 - 0))))}{(2 \times (17 - (3 - 5)))} := \frac{((8 \times (6 - 9)) + 40)}{(2 \times (1 - (7 - (3 + 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (1 \times (7 - (3 - 5))))}{(((8 - 6)^9) \times (4 - 0))} := \frac{(2 \times (1 \times (7 + (3 - 5))))}{(8 - ((6 - 9) \times 40))} := \frac{2 \times 1^{735}}{8^{6-9+4+0}} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + ((1 + (7 - 3)) \times 5))}{(8 + (6 + (94 - 0)))} := \frac{(2 + ((1 + 7) \times (3^5)))}{(8 + (6^{9-4+0}))} := \frac{(2 + (1 - (7 \times (3 - 5))))}{(8 + ((6 + 9) \times (4 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (1 - (7 - 35)))}{((8 \times (6 + 9)) + (4 - 0))} := \frac{(2 + (1 \times ((7 \times 3) + 5)))}{(8 \times ((6 \times 9) - 40))} := \frac{(2 + (1 \times ((7 - 3) \times 5)))}{(8 \times (6 + (9 - (4 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((8 \times (6 + 9)) + (4 - 0))}{(2 + (1 \times (7 - (3 - 5))))} := \frac{(8 \times ((6 \times 9) - 40))}{(2 + (1 \times (7 \times (3 \times 5))))} := \frac{(8 \times (6 + (9 - (4 - 0))))}{(2 + (1 \times (7 \times 35)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((8 - (6 - 9)) \times (4 - 0))}{(2 + (1 \times (7 + (3 \times 5))))} := \frac{((8 \times (6 \times 9)) - (4 - 0))}{2 + 1^{735}} := \frac{((8 \times 6) + 940)}{(2 + (1 + (7 + (3 - 5))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 - (6 - (94 - 0)))}{(2 + (1 + (7 + 35)))} := \frac{((8 \times 6) - (9 \times (4 - 0)))}{(2 + (1 + (73 - 5)))} := \frac{((8 - 6)^{9-4+0})}{(2 + (173 + 5))} \\
 &:= \frac{(86 + (94 - 0))}{(2 + 1735)} := \frac{(8 + (69 \times (4 - 0)))}{(21 + (7 \times (3 + 5)))} := \frac{((8 - 6) \times (9 \times 40))}{((8 + 69) \times (4 - 0))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{31485}{62970} := \frac{(((3 - (1 - 4)) \times 8) + 5)}{(((6 - 2) \times 9) + 70)} := \frac{(((3 + 1) \times 48) + 5)}{(((6^2) \times 9) + 70)} := \frac{((3 - ((1^4)^8))^5)}{(62 + (9 - (7 - 0)))}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((3 - (1^4)) \times (8 + 5))}{(((6^2) + (9 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{((3 \times (1 + 4)) + 85)}{(6 + (2 \times (97 - 0)))} := \frac{((3 \times (14 + 8)) + 5)}{(((6 + 2) \times 9) + 70)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times 14) + (8 \times 5))}{(6 + (2 \times (9 + 70)))} := \frac{((3 \times 14) + 85)}{(((6^2) \times 9) - 70)} := \frac{((3 + (1 \times 4)) \times 85)}{((6 + (2 + 9)) \times 70)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 + (1^4)) \times (8 + 5))}{((6 \times 29) - 70)} := \frac{((3 + 1) \times ((4 \times 8) - 5))}{(6 \times (29 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{((3 + 1) \times 485)}{((6 - 2) \times 970)} \\
 &:= \frac{((31 + 4) \times (8 + 5))}{((6 - (2 - 9)) \times 70)} := \frac{(3 - ((1 - (4 \times 8)) \times 5))}{(((6 - 2) \times (9 + 70))} := \frac{(3 - (1 - ((4 \times 8) - 5)))}{(6 - ((2 \times 9) - 70))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(3 - (1 - ((4 + 8) \times 5)))}{(62 \times (9 - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 - (1 - (4 \times (8 - 5))))}{(6 + (29 - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 - (1 - (4^{8-5})))}{(6 + (2 \times (9 \times (7 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (1 - (4 + (8 + 5))))}{(6 + (2 \times (9 + (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(3 - (1 \times ((4 - 8) \times 5)))}{(62 - (9 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 - (1 \times (4 - (8 + 5))))}{(6 \times (2^{9-7+0}))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (1 \times (4 - 85)))}{((6 + (2 \times 9)) \times (7 - 0))} := \frac{(3 - (1 + (4 - (8 - 5))))}{(6 - (2^{9-7+0}))} := \frac{(3 - (1 - 485))}{(6 - (2 - 970))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (((1 + 4) \times 8) - 5))}{(((6 \times 2) - 9) \times 70)} := \frac{(3 \times ((1 - (4 - 8)) \times 5))}{(6 \times ((2 \times 9) + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 \times ((1 + 48) \times 5))}{(((6 \times 2) + 9) \times 70)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times ((14 \times 8) - 5))}{((6 \times 2) + (9 \times 70))} := \frac{(3 \times (1 - (4 - (8 + 5))))}{(62 - (9 - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 \times (1 \times (4 \times (8 - 5))))}{((6^2) \times (9 - (7 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (1 \times (4 + (8 - 5))))}{(6 + (29 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 \times (1 + (4 \times (8 - 5))))}{(62 + (9 + (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 \times (1 + (4^{8-5})))}{(6 \times (2 + (9 \times (7 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (1 + (4 + (8 + 5))))}{(6 \times (2 + (9 + (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(3 \times (14 - (8 - 5)))}{(6 \times ((2 \times 9) - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 \times (14 \times (8 - 5)))}{((6 - 2) \times (9 \times (7 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (14 + 85))}{(6 \times (2 + (97 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 \times (1^{485}))}{(6 - (2 - (9 - (7 - 0))))} := \frac{(3 + (((1^4)^8) \times 5))}{((6 - 2)^{9-7+0})} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + ((1^4) + (8 + 5)))}{((6^2) - (9 - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 + ((1^4) + (8 - 5)))}{((6 \times 2) + (9 - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 + ((1^4) + 85))}{((6 \times (2 \times 9)) + 70)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + ((1 + 48) \times 5))}{(6 - ((2 - 9) \times 70))} := \frac{(3 + (1 \times (4 + (8 \times 5))))}{(6 + ((2 \times 9) + 70))} := \frac{(3 + (1 \times (4 + (8 - 5))))}{(6 - (2 - (9 + (7 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (1 \times (48 \times 5)))}{(6 \times (2 + (9 + 70)))} := \frac{(3 + (1^{485}))}{((6 - 2) \times (9 - (7 - 0)))} := \frac{(3 + (1 + ((4 + 8) \times 5)))}{(6 - (2 \times (9 - 70)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (1 + (4 - (8 - 5))))}{(6 + (2^{9-7+0}))} := \frac{(3 + (1 + (4^{8-5})))}{((6 \times (2 + 9)) + 70)} := \frac{(3 + (1 + (48 \times 5)))}{((62 \times 9) - 70)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (1 + 485))}{(6 + (2 + 970))} := \frac{(3 + 1485)}{(6 + 2970)} := \frac{(31 + 485)}{(62 + 970)} \\
 &:= \frac{(314 - (8 - 5))}{(629 - (7 - 0))} := \frac{(314 + (8 - 5))}{(6 - (2 - (9 \times 70)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.55 57 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10469}{83752} &:= \frac{(((1 - (0 - 4)) \times 6) - 9)}{(8 \times (3 - (7 - (5^2))))} := \frac{(((1 - (0 - 4))^6) \times 9)}{(8 \times (375^2))} := \frac{(((1^{04}) + 6) \times 9)}{(8 \times (3 \times (7 \times (5 - 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((1 - (0 - (4 \times 6))) \times 9)}{(8 \times ((3 + (7 + 5))^2))} := \frac{(((1 - (0 - (4 + 6))) \times 9)}{(8 \times (3 \times ((7 \times 5) - 2)))} := \frac{((1^{04}) - (6 - 9))}{(8 + (3 + (7 \times (5 - 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1^{04}) + 69)}{(8 \times ((3 + 7) \times (5 + 2)))} := \frac{(((1 + (0 - (4 - 6))) \times 9)}{(8 \times (3 + ((7 + 5) \times 2)))} := \frac{((10 \times (4 \times 6)) + 9)}{(83 \times ((7 + 5) \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{((10 \times (4 \times 6)) - 9)}{(8 \times (3 \times (75 + 2)))} := \frac{(((10 + (4 - 6)) \times 9)}{(8 \times (3 \times ((7 + 5) \times 2)))} := \frac{((10 + (4 - 6))^9)}{8^{(3+7-5) \times 2}} \\
 &:= \frac{((10 + 4) \times (6 + 9))}{(8 \times (3 \times (7 \times (5 \times 2))))} := \frac{(1 - ((0 \times 46) - 9))}{(8 \times ((3 + (7 - 5)) \times 2))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - ((4 \times 6) + 9)))}{(8 \times ((3 \times (7 + 5)) - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - ((4 \times 6) - 9)))}{(83 - (7 - 52))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (4 - (6 - 9))))}{(8 - (3 - (7 + 52)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (4 \times (6 + 9))))}{((8^3) - ((7 + 5) \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (4 + (6 + 9))))}{(8 \times (3 + (7 + (5 \times 2))))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (4 + (6 - 9))))}{(8 \times ((3 - (7 - 5)) \times 2))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (46 + 9)))}{(((83 + 7) \times 5) - 2)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (46 - 9)))}{(8 \times ((3 \times (7 + 5)) + 2))} := \frac{(1 - (0 \times (4 - 69)))}{(8 - (3 \times (7 - (5 + 2))))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - 469))}{(8 + 3752)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((0 - (4 - 6))^9))}{8^{3 \times (7-5)-2}} := \frac{(1 \times ((0 \times 4) - (6 - 9)))}{(8 \times (3 - (7 - (5 + 2))))} := \frac{(1 \times ((0 \times 46) + 9))}{(8 - ((3 - (7 \times 5)) \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 - ((4 - 6) \times 9)))}{(8 \times ((3^{7-5}) \times 2))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 - (4 - (6 \times 9))))}{(((8 + (3 - 7)) \times 5)^2)} := \frac{(1 \times (0 - (4 - (6 + 9))))}{(8 + (3 + (75 + 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 - (4 \times (6 - 9))))}{(8 \times (3 \times (7 - (5 - 2))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((4 \times 6) + 9)))}{(8 + (((3 \times 7) - 5)^2)} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((4 \times 6) - 9)))}{((8 - (3 - 7)) \times (5 \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((4 + 6) \times 9)))}{((8 - 3) \times ((7 + 5)^2))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (4 - (6 - 9))))}{(8 + (3 - (7 - 52)))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (4 \times (6 \times 9))))}{((8 - (3 - 7))^{5-2})} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (4 \times (6 + 9))))}{((8^3) - (7 + (5^2)))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (4 + (6 + 9))))}{(8 - ((3 - 75) \times 2))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (4 + 69)))}{(8 \times (3 + (7 \times (5 \times 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (46 + 9)))}{(8 + (3 \times ((7 + 5)^2))} := \frac{(1 + (0 - (4 - (6 \times 9))))}{(8 \times (3 \times (7 + (5 \times 2))))} := \frac{(1 + (0 - (4 \times (6 - 9))))}{(8 + (3 \times (7 + (5^2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (4 - 69)))}{(8 + ((3 + 7) \times 52))} := \frac{(10 - ((4 - 6) \times 9))}{(8 \times ((3 \times 7) + (5 + 2)))} := \frac{(10 \times ((4 + 6)^9))}{(8 \times (((3 + 7)^5)^2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 \times (46 + 9))}{((8 + ((3^7) + 5)) \times 2)} := \frac{(10 \times (46 - 9))}{(8 \times (37 \times (5 \times 2)))} := \frac{10^{4-6+9}}{(8 \times ((3 + 7)^{5+2}))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 + ((4 \times 6) - 9))}{(8 \times ((3 + (7 - 5))^2))} := \frac{(10 + ((4 + 6) \times 9))}{(8 \times ((3 + 7) \times (5 \times 2)))} := \frac{(10 + (4 - (6 - 9)))}{(8 \times (3 + (7 + (5 + 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 + (4 + (6 \times 9)))}{((8^3) + (7 + (5^2)))} := \frac{(10 + (46 - 9))}{(8 \times (37 + (5 \times 2)))} := \frac{(104 - (6 + 9))}{(8 \times (37 + 52))} \\
 &:= \frac{(104 - (6 - 9))}{(8 \times ((3 \times (7 \times 5)) + 2))} := \frac{(104 + (6 \times 9))}{((8^3) + 752)} := \frac{(104 - 69)}{(8 \times (3 + (7 + (5^2))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.56 58 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14865}{29730} &:= \frac{(((1 - (4 - 8)) \times 6) - 5)}{(2 + ((9 + 7) \times (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(((14 + 8) \times 6) - 5)}{(2 \times (97 + 30))} := \frac{(((1 - (4 - (8 + 6))) \times 5)}{((2 + 9) \times (7 + (3 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((1 - (4 - 8)) \times (6 \times 5))}{(297 + (3 - 0))} := \frac{(((1^4) + (8 \times (6 \times 5)))}{(2 + ((9 + 7) \times 30))} := \frac{(((1^4) + (8 + (6^5))))}{(((2^9) + 7) \times 30)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((1 + ((4 \times 8) - 6))^5)}{(2 \times ((9^7) \times (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(((14 \times 8) - (6 \times 5))}{(2 \times (9 + (73 - 0)))} := \frac{(((14 \times 8) + 65)}{(2 + (9 + (7^3 + 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((14 - 8) \times (6 + 5))}{(2 \times ((9 \times 7) + (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 - ((4 - (8 + 6)) \times 5))}{(2 + (97 + (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 - ((4 \times 8) - 65))}{(2 + ((9 \times 7) + (3 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (4 - ((8 + 6) \times 5)))}{(2 \times (97 - 30))} := \frac{(1 - (4 - (8 - (6 - 5))))}{(2 + ((9 - 7) \times (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 - (4 - (8 \times (6 - 5))))}{(2 \times (9 - (7 - (3 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (4 - (8 + (6 + 5))))}{2^{9-7+3+0}} := \frac{(1 - (4 - (8 + (6 - 5))))}{(2 \times ((9 - 7) \times (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(1 - (4 + (8 - (6 \times 5))))}{(2 + (9 \times (7 - (3 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (4 + (8 - 65)))}{((29 + 7) \times (3 - 0))} := \frac{(1 \times ((4 \times (8 - 6)) - 5))}{(29 + (7 - 30))} := \frac{(1 \times ((4 + (8 + 6)) \times 5))}{(2 \times (9 \times (7 + (3 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((4 + (8 - 6)) \times 5))}{(2 \times (9 + (7 \times (3 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 \times ((48 + 6) \times 5))}{((2 + (9 + 7)) \times 30)} := \frac{(1 \times (4 - (8 - (6 \times 5))))}{(29 - (7 - 30))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 - (8 - (6 + 5))))}{(2 - (9 - (7 \times (3 - 0))))} := \frac{(1 \times (4 \times ((8 - 6) \times 5)))}{((2 + 9) \times 7) + (3 - 0)} := \frac{(1 \times (4 \times ((8 - 6)^5)))}{2^{9-7^3} + 0} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 \times (8 \times (6 + 5))))}{(2 \times (9 + (7^3 + 0)))} := \frac{(1 \times (4 \times (8 \times (6 - 5))))}{(2 \times (9 - (7 - 30)))} := \frac{(1 \times (4 \times (8 + (6 - 5))))}{(2 \times (9 \times (7 - (3 - 0))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{1 \times 4^{8-6+5}}{((2 \times (9+7))^3 + 0)} &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 + (8 - (6 - 5))))}{((2 \times 9) + (7 - (3 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 + (8 + (6 \times 5))))}{(2 + (9 + (73 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{1^{4865}}{((2 \times (9+7)) - 30)} &:= \frac{(1 + ((4^{8-6}) + 5))}{((2+9) \times (7 - (3 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 + ((4 + (8 \times 6)) \times 5))}{((2^9) + (7 + (3 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + ((4 + (8 - 6)) \times 5))}{(2 + ((9 - 7) \times 30))} &:= \frac{(1 + ((4 + 8) \times (6 \times 5)))}{((2^9) + (7 \times 30))} &:= \frac{(1 + (4 - (8 - (6 \times 5))))}{((2 + (9 + 7)) \times (3 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (4 - (8 - (6 + 5))))}{(2 - (9 + (7 - 30)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (4 \times (8 \times (6 - 5))))}{(2 - (9 - (73 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (4 \times (8 + (6 - 5))))}{(((2 + 9) \times 7) - (3 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (4 + ((8 \times 6) + 5)))}{(29 \times (7 - (3 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (4 + ((8 \times 6) - 5)))}{(2 + (97 - (3 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (4 + ((8 - 6) \times 5)))}{(2 - (9 - (7 + 30)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (4 + (8 \times (6 + 5))))}{(2 \times ((9 \times 7) + 30))} &:= \frac{(1 + (4 + (8 \times (6 - 5))))}{(2 \times (9 + (7 - (3 - 0))))} &:= \frac{(1 + (4 + (8 + (6 + 5))))}{(2 + (9 + (7 + 30)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (4 + (8 + (6 - 5))))}{((2 \times 9) + (7 + (3 - 0)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (4 + (8 + 65)))}{((2 \times (9 \times 7)) + 30)} &:= \frac{(1 + (48 + (6 + 5)))}{(2 \times ((9 - 7) \times 30))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (48 + 65))}{((2 \times 9) + (7 \times 30))} &:= \frac{(1 + 4865)}{(2 + 9730)} &:= \frac{(14 - (8 - (6 + 5)))}{(2 + (9 - (7 - 30)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(14 \times (8 \times (6 - 5)))}{((2 \times 97) + 30)} &:= \frac{(14 + ((8 - 6)^5))}{(2 \times (9 + (7 + 30)))} &:= \frac{(14 + (8 \times (6 \times 5)))}{((2^9) - (7 - (3 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(148 - (6 - 5))}{(297 - (3 - 0))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► **15237**
60948

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((1+5)^2) \times (3^7))}{(6 \times (0 + ((9^4) \times 8)))} &:= \frac{(((1 - (5 - (2^3))))^7)}{((6 \times (0 \times 9)) + (4^8))} &:= \frac{((1 + (5 - (2 - 3))) \times 7)}{(((60 - 9) \times 4) - 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (5 \times 2)) \times (3 + 7))}{((60 - (9 - 4)) \times 8)} &:= \frac{((1 + (5 + (2 \times 3))) \times 7)}{((6 - (0 - (9 \times 4))) \times 8)} &:= \frac{((1 + (5 + (2 + 3))) \times 7)}{((60 \times (9 - 4)) + 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (5 + 23)) \times 7)}{(60 + (94 \times 8))} &:= \frac{((1 + 5) \times (2 \times (3 + 7)))}{((6 - (0 - 9)) \times (4 \times 8))} &:= \frac{((1 + 5) \times (2 + (3 \times 7)))}{((60 \times 9) + (4 + 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + 5) \times (2 + (3^7)))}{((6 - (0 - (9^4))) \times 8)} &:= \frac{((1 + 5) \times (2 + (3 + 7)))}{(6 \times ((0 \times 9) + 48))} &:= \frac{((1 + 5) \times 237)}{(6 \times (0 + 948))} \\
 &:= \frac{((15 \times 2) + 37)}{(((60 + 9) \times 4) - 8)} &:= \frac{((15 - 2) \times (3 + 7))}{((60 + (9 - 4)) \times 8)} &:= \frac{(1 - ((5 - 23) \times 7))}{((60 \times 9) - (4 \times 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (5 - ((2^3) \times 7)))}{((6 \times (0 + (9 \times 4))) - 8)} &:= \frac{(1 - (5 - (2 - (3 - 7))))}{((6 \times (0 \times 94)) + 8)} &:= \frac{(1 - (5 - (2 \times (3 \times 7))))}{((6 - (0 - (9 + 4))) \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((5 - (2 - 3)) \times 7))}{(6 \times (0 + ((9 \times 4) - 8)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((5 \times (2 \times 3)) - 7))}{(6 - (0 - (94 - 8)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((5 + 2) \times (3 \times 7)))}{((60 \times 9) + 48)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (5 - (2 - (3 \times 7))))}{(60 - (9 \times (4 - 8)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (5 - (2 \times (3 - 7))))}{(((6 - (0 - 9)) \times 4) - 8)} &:= \frac{(1 \times (5 \times ((2^3) + 7)))}{(60 \times (9 + (4 - 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (5 \times (2 \times (3 + 7))))}{(((6 \times (0 + 9)) - 4) \times 8)} &:= \frac{(1 \times (5 \times (2 + (3 + 7))))}{(6 \times (0 + ((9 - 4) \times 8)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (5 \times (2 + 37)))}{(60 \times (9 - (4 - 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (5^{23-7}))}{(60 - ((9 - 4) \times 8))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (5 + ((2^3) + 7)))}{((6 - ((0 \times 9) - 4)) \times 8)} &:= \frac{(1 \times (5 + (2 \times (3 + 7))))}{(60 + ((9 - 4) \times 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (5 + (2 + (3 + 7))))}{(((6 - (0 - 9)) \times 4) + 8)} &:= \frac{(1 \times (5 + (2 + (3 - 7))))}{((6 + (0 - 9)) \times (4 - 8))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (52 - (3 - 7)))}{((6 \times (0 + (9 \times 4))) + 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (52 + (3 \times 7)))}{((60 \times (9 - 4)) - 8)} &:= \frac{1^{5237}}{((6 \times (0 \times 9)) - (4 - 8))} &:= \frac{(1 + ((5 \times 23) + 7))}{(60 + (9 \times 48))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + ((5 + (2 + 3)) \times 7))}{(((60 + 9) \times 4) + 8)} &:= \frac{(1 + ((5 + 23) \times 7))}{((60 \times (9 + 4)) + 8)} &:= \frac{(1 + ((5 - 2) \times (3 \times 7)))}{((6 + ((0 \times 9) - 4))^8)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(1 + (5 - (2 + (3 - 7))))}{((6 \times ((0 \times 9) + 4)) + 8)} := \frac{(1 + (5 - (2 - 37)))}{(60 + ((9 + 4) \times 8))} := \frac{(1 + (5 \times ((2 \times 3) + 7)))}{(6 \times (0 + ((9 \times 4) + 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (5 \times (2 + (3 \times 7))))}{(((6 \times (0 + 9)) + 4) \times 8)} := \frac{(1 + (5^{2^3-7}))}{(6 \times ((0 \times 9) - (4 - 8)))} := \frac{(1 + (5 + (2 - (3 - 7))))}{(6 \times ((0 \times 94) + 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (5 + (2 \times (3 \times 7))))}{(6 \times ((0 \times 9) + (4 \times 8)))} := \frac{(1 + (5 + (2 \times (3 + 7))))}{(60 + ((9 \times 4) + 8))} := \frac{(1 + (5 + (2 + (3 + 7))))}{(6 \times ((0 \times 9) + (4 + 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (5 + (2 + (3 - 7))))}{((6 + ((0 \times 9) - 4)) \times 8)} := \frac{(1 + (5 + (2 + 37)))}{((6 - (0 - 9)) \times (4 + 8))} := \frac{(1 + (5 + (23 - 7)))}{((6 - (0 - (9 - 4))) \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(15 \times (2 + (3 + 7)))}{((6 - (0 - 9)) \times 48)} := \frac{(15 + (2 + (3 + 7)))}{(6 - (0 - (94 + 8)))} := \frac{(15 + (2 + 37))}{(6 \times (0 - (9 \times (4 - 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(15 + 237)}{(60 + 948)} := \frac{(152 - (3 - 7))}{(6 \times (0 + ((9 + 4) \times 8)))} := \frac{(152 + (3 + 7))}{(6 \times (0 + (9 \times (4 + 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1523 + 7)}{(60 \times (94 + 8))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{20439}{81756}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((2 - (0 - 4))^3) - 9)}{(817 + (5 + 6))} := \frac{(((2^{04}) \times 3) - 9)}{((81 \times (7 - 5)) - 6)} := \frac{((2 - (0 - (4 + 3))) \times 9)}{(((8 - 1) \times 7) + 5) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 - (0 - (4 - 3))) \times 9)}{((8 + 1) \times ((7 - 5) \times 6))} := \frac{((2 - (0 - 4)) \times (3 \times 9))}{(8 \times (1 \times (75 + 6)))} := \frac{((2 - (0 - 4)) \times (3 + 9))}{(8 \times (((1^7) + 5) \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 - (0 - 4)) \times 39)}{((81 + 75) \times 6)} := \frac{((2 \times (0 \times 43)) + 9)}{((2 \times (0 \times 43)) + 9)} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + (4 \times 3))) - 9)}{((2 \times (0 + (4 \times 3))) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (0 + (4 + 3))) - 9)}{(8 + (1 \times ((7 - 5) \times 6)))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + 4)) - (3 - 9))}{(8 - (1 + (7 - 56)))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + 4)) + (3 \times 9))}{(8 + ((17 + 5) \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (0 + 4)) + 39)}{(8 - ((1 - 7) \times (5 \times 6)))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 - 4)) + (3 \times 9))}{(8 - (1 - (75 - 6)))} := \frac{((2^{04}) - (3 - 9))}{(8 - (1 - (75 + 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^{04}) \times (3 \times 9))}{(8 \times ((1 + (7 \times 5)) \times 6))} := \frac{((2^{04}) + (3 + 9))}{((8 + (1 - 7)) \times 56)} := \frac{((20 \times 4) - (3 \times 9))}{(8 - ((1 - (7 \times 5)) \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{((20 \times 4) + (3 + 9))}{(8 \times (((1 + 7) \times 5) + 6))} := \frac{((20 \times 4) + (3 - 9))}{(8 \times (1 \times (7 + (5 \times 6))))} := \frac{((20 + (4 + 3)) \times 9)}{(81 \times ((7 - 5) \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - ((0 \times 43) - 9))}{(8 - (1 - (7 + (5 \times 6))))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - ((4^3) - 9)))}{(8 - ((1 - 7) \times 5)) \times 6)} := \frac{(2 - (0 - ((4 - 3)^9)))}{(8 - (1 \times (7 - (5 + 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (4 - (3 - 9))))}{(8 \times (1 \times (7 + (5 - 6))))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (4 \times 39)))}{(8 \times ((17 \times 5) - 6))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (4 + (3 + 9))))}{(8 + (1 + (7 + 56)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (4 + 39)))}{((8 + (17 + 5)) \times 6)} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (43 - 9)))}{(8 \times (1 \times (7 + (5 + 6))))} := \frac{(2 - (0 \times (4 - 39)))}{(8 \times (1^{756}))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 + 1756)}{(2 \times (0 - (4 \times (3 - 9))))} := \frac{(2 \times ((0 \times 4) + (3 + 9)))}{(8 \times (1 \times ((7 - 5) \times 6)))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 - (4 - (3 + 9))))}{(8 \times (1 \times (7 - (5 - 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(8 \times (1 - (7 - (5 \times 6))))}{(2 \times (0 + ((4 \times 3) + 9)))} := \frac{((81 \times (7 - 5)) + 6)}{(2 \times (0 + ((4 \times 3) - 9)))} := \frac{(8 + (17 + (5 - 6)))}{(8 \times (17 + (5 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + ((4^3) + 9)))}{(8 \times (1 + ((7 + 5) \times 6)))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + ((4 + 3) \times 9)))}{(8 \times (1 \times (7 + 56)))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (4 - (3 - 9))))}{(8 + (1 \times ((7 + 5) \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (4 \times (3 + 9))))}{((8 \times (1 \times (7 - 5))) \times 6)} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (4 + (3 \times 9))))}{(8 \times ((1^7) + (5 \times 6)))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (4 + (3 + 9))))}{(8 \times (17 + (5 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (4 + 39)))}{(8 - ((1 - 7) \times 56))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (43 - 9)))}{(8 \times (((1 + 7) \times 5) - 6))} := \frac{2^{-04-3+9}}{(8 + (1 \times (7 - (5 - 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{2^{04 \times 3 - 9}}{(8 + (1 - (7 - (5 \times 6))))} := \frac{(2 + (0 - ((4 - 3)^9)))}{(8 + (1 \times (7 - (5 + 6))))} := \frac{(2 + (0 - (4 - (3 + 9))))}{(8 \times (1 - (7 - (5 + 6))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(2 + (0 - (4 \times (3 - 9))))}{(8 \times (1 + ((7 - 5) \times 6)))} := \frac{(20 - (4 \times (3 - 9)))}{((8 + (1 + 7)) \times (5 + 6))} := \frac{(20 \times ((4 \times 3) + 9))}{(8 \times (1 \times (7 \times (5 \times 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(20 \times ((4 \times 3) - 9))}{(8 \times (1 + ((7 \times 5) - 6)))} := \frac{(20 + ((4 - 3)^9))}{(8 - (1 - (7 \times (5 + 6))))} := \frac{(20 + (4 - (3 - 9)))}{((8 + (1 \times (7 + 5))) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(20 + (4 \times (3 \times 9)))}{(8 \times (1 + (7 + 56)))} := \frac{(20 + (4 \times 39))}{(8 \times ((1 + 7) \times (5 + 6)))} := \frac{(20 + (4 + 39))}{((8 - (1 - (7 \times 5))) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(204 - (3 - 9))}{((8 + (1 \times 7)) \times 56)}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.57 59 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{13548}{27096} &:= \frac{(((1 - (3 - 5))^4) - 8)}{(2 \times (70 + (9 - 6)))} := \frac{1^3 \times (5 - 4) \times 8}{2^{7-09+6}} := \frac{1^3 \times (5 - 4) + 8}{(2 + (70 - (9 \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1^3) \times ((5^4) + 8))}{((2 \times (70 \times 9)) + 6)} := \frac{((1^3) + (5 + 48))}{((2 + (7 - (0 - 9))) \times 6)} := \frac{((1 + (3 \times 5)) \times (4^8))}{((2^7 + 0)^{9-6})} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (3 \times (5 - 4))) \times 8)}{(2^{7 \times 0 \times 9 + 6})} := \frac{((1 + (3 + (5 \times 4))) \times 8)}{((2^7 + 0) \times (9 - 6))} := \frac{((1 + (3 + 5)) \times (4 + 8))}{((2 + 70) \times (9 - 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 48))}{((2^7 + 0) \times (9 + 6))} := \frac{((1 + 35) \times (4 + 8))}{((2 + (7 - 0)) \times 96)} := \frac{(1 - ((3 \times 5) - 48))}{((2 \times (7 - 0)) + (9 \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (3 - ((5 - 4) \times 8)))}{(2 + (7 - (0 - (9 - 6))))} := \frac{(1 - (3 - (5 - (4 - 8))))}{(2 \times (7 - (0 \times 96)))} := \frac{(1 - (3 - (5 \times (4 + 8))))}{((2 \times (70 - 9)) - 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (3 - (5 \times 48)))}{(2 + ((70 + 9) \times 6))} := \frac{(1 - (3 - (5 + (4 + 8))))}{((2 \times (7 - 0)) - 9) \times 6} := \frac{(1 - (3 - (54 + 8)))}{((2 \times (7 \times (0 + 9))) - 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (3 \times (5 - (4 \times 8))))}{((2 \times (70 + 9)) + 6)} := \frac{(1 - (3 \times (5 - (4 + 8))))}{(2 \times (7 - (0 - (9 + 6))))} := \frac{(1 - (3 \times (5 \times (4 - 8))))}{(2 \times (7 - (0 - (9 \times 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (35 - 48))}{(2 - (70 - 96))} := \frac{(1 \times ((3 - (5 - 4)) \times 8))}{(2 \times (70 - (9 \times 6)))} := \frac{(1 \times ((3 \times (5 + 4)) - 8))}{((2 \times (7 - (0 - 9))) + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((3^5) - 48))}{((2 - (7 \times (0 - 9))) \times 6)} := \frac{(1 \times ((3 + (5 \times 4)) \times 8))}{(2 + ((70 - 9) \times 6))} := \frac{(1 \times ((3 + (5 + 4)) \times 8))}{(2 \times ((7 - (0 - 9)) \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((3 + 5) \times 48))}{((2^{7+0 \times 9}) \times 6)} := \frac{(1 \times (3 - (5 - (4 + 8))))}{(2 \times (7 - (0 - (9 - 6))))} := \frac{(1 \times (3 \times ((5 \times 4) + 8)))}{(2 + (70 + 96))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (3 \times (5 - (4 - 8))))}{((2 + (7 - (0 \times 9))) \times 6)} := \frac{(1 \times (3 \times (54 \times 8)))}{(27 \times (0 + 96))} := \frac{(1 \times (3^{5+4-8}))}{(2 + (7 + (0 - (9 - 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (3 + ((5^4) + 8)))}{(2 \times ((70 \times 9) + 6))} := \frac{(1 \times (3 + (5 - (4 - 8))))}{(2 + (7 - (0 - (9 + 6))))} := \frac{(1 \times (3 + (5 \times (4 + 8))))}{(2 + (70 + (9 \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (3 + (5 \times 48)))}{((2 + (70 + 9)) \times 6)} := \frac{(1 \times (3 + (54 - 8)))}{(2 + ((7 - (0 - 9)) \times 6))} := \frac{(1 \times (35 + (4 \times 8)))}{((2^{7+0 \times 9}) + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{1^{3548}}{(2 - (7 \times (0 \times 96)))} := \frac{(1 + ((3 \times (5 \times 4)) + 8))}{(2 \times ((7 \times (0 + 9)) + 6))} := \frac{(1 + ((3^5) + (4 - 8)))}{((2 - 7) \times (0 - 96))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + ((3 + (5 + 4)) \times 8))}{((2 \times 70) + (9 \times 6))} := \frac{(1 + ((35 + 4) \times 8))}{(2 + ((70 \times 9) - 6))} := \frac{(1 + (3 \times ((5 \times 4) + 8)))}{(2 \times (70 + (9 + 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (3 \times ((5 \times 4) - 8)))}{((2^7 + 0) - (9 \times 6))} := \frac{(1 + (3 \times (5 + (4 \times 8))))}{((2^7 + 0) + 96)} := \frac{(1 + (3^{5+4-8}))}{(2 \times (7 + (0 - (9 - 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (3 + ((5 + 4) \times 8)))}{((2 \times (70 + 9)) - 6)} := \frac{(1 + (3 + (5 - (4 - 8))))}{((2 \times (7 - (0 - 9))) - 6)} := \frac{(1 + (3 + (5 \times (4 + 8))))}{2^7 + 0 \times 96}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(1 + (3 + (5 + (4 + 8))))}{(2 \times (7 \times (0 + (9 - 6))))} := \frac{(1 + (3 + (5 + (4 - 8))))}{(2 - (7 + (0 - (9 + 6))))} := \frac{(1 + (3 + (5 + 48)))}{(2 \times ((7 \times (0 + 9)) - 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (3 + (54 + 8)))}{((2 \times (7 \times (0 + 9))) + 6)} := \frac{(1 + 3548)}{(2 + 7096)} := \frac{(135 - (4 \times 8))}{(2 \times (7 - (0 - 96)))} \\ &:= \frac{135 + 48}{270 + 96} := \frac{135 - 48}{270 - 96} \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{14538}{29076}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(((1 + 4) \times (5 \times 3)) - 8)}{(2 + (90 + (7 \times 6)))} := \frac{(((1 + 4) \times (5^3)) + 8)}{((2 \times (90 \times 7)) + 6)} := \frac{((1 - ((4 - 5) \times 3)) \times 8)}{2^{9 \times 0 \times 7 + 6}} \\ &:= \frac{((1^4) \times (5 \times 38))}{(2 - (9 \times (0 - (7 \times 6))))} := \frac{((1 + (4 \times 5)) \times (3 + 8))}{((2 + (9 - 0)) \times (7 \times 6))} := \frac{((1 + 4) \times (5 + (3 \times 8)))}{(290 \times (7 - 6))} \\ &:= \frac{((1 + 4) \times (5 + (3 + 8)))}{((2 \times (90 - 7)) - 6)} := \frac{((14 \times (5 \times 3)) + 8)}{((2^9 + 0) - 76)} := \frac{((14 \times 5) + (3 \times 8))}{((2 \times (90 + 7)) - 6)} \\ &:= \frac{((14 \times 5) + 38)}{((29 - (0 - 7)) \times 6)} := \frac{(1 - ((4 - (5 \times 3)) \times 8))}{(2 \times (90 - (7 - 6)))} := \frac{(1 - ((4 + 5) \times (3 - 8)))}{(2 + (90 \times (7 - 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (4 - ((5 - 3)^8)))}{2^{9+0 \times 7} - 6} := \frac{(1 - (4 - (5 - (3 - 8))))}{(2 + ((9 + (0 - 7)) \times 6))} := \frac{(1 - (4 - (5 \times (3 + 8))))}{((2 \times 90) - 76)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (4 - (5 + (3 + 8))))}{((2 \times (9 - (0 - 7))) - 6)} := \frac{(1 - (4 \times (5 - (3 \times 8))))}{(2 \times (90 - (7 + 6)))} := \frac{(1 - (4 \times (5 - (3 + 8))))}{(2 + (90 - (7 \times 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (4 + (5 - (3 + 8))))}{(2 - (9 + (0 - (7 + 6))))} := \frac{(1 - (4 + (5 \times (3 - 8))))}{(2 \times (9 - (0 - (7 + 6))))} := \frac{(1 - (4 + (5 - 38)))}{((2 \times (9 - 0)) + (7 \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (((4 + 5) \times 3) - 8))}{((2 \times (9 - (0 - 7))) + 6)} := \frac{(1 \times ((4 - (5 - 3))^8))}{2^{9+0 \times 76}} := \frac{(1 \times ((4 \times (5 - 3))^8))}{(2 \times ((9 - (0 - 7))^6))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times ((4^5 - 3) \times 8))}{2^{9-07+6}} := \frac{(1 \times ((4^5 - 3) - 8))}{(2 \times (9 + (0 - (7 - 6))))} := \frac{(1 \times ((4 + (5 + 3)) \times 8))}{(2 \times ((9 - (0 - 7)) \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 - (5 - (3 + 8))))}{(2 \times (9 - (0 - (7 - 6))))} := \frac{(1 \times (4 - (5 + (3 - 8))))}{2^{9+0 \times 7-6}} := \frac{(1 \times (4 \times ((5 \times 3) - 8)))}{(2 - (9 \times ((0 \times 7) - 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 \times (5 + (3 + 8))))}{(2 \times ((9 + (0 - 7))^6))} := \frac{(1 \times (4 + (5 - (3 - 8))))}{(2 \times (90 - 76))} := \frac{(1 \times (4 + (5 \times (3 \times 8))))}{(290 - (7 \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 + (5 + (3 \times 8))))}{(2 + ((9 + (0 - 7))^6))} := \frac{(1 \times (4 + (5 + 38)))}{((2 \times (9 - 0)) + 76)} := \frac{(1 \times (4 + (53 - 8)))}{(2 + ((9 - (0 - 7)) \times 6))} \\ &:= \frac{1^{4538}}{(2 - (9 \times (0 \times 76)))} := \frac{(1 + ((4^5 - 3) - 8))}{(2 \times (9 - (0 \times 76)))} := \frac{(1 + ((4 + 5) \times (3 + 8)))}{((2 \times (90 + 7)) + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + ((4 + 5) \times 38))}{(2 - (9 \times (0 - 76)))} := \frac{(1 + ((4 - 5) \times (3 - 8)))}{(2 + (9 - (0 - (7 - 6))))} := \frac{(1 + (4 - (5 + (3 - 8))))}{(2 + (9 + (0 - (7 - 6))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (4 \times (5 + (3 \times 8))))}{(2 \times (9 \times (0 + (7 + 6))))} := \frac{(1 + (4 + ((5 \times 3) - 8)))}{(2 + (9 - (0 - (7 + 6))))} := \frac{(1 + (4 + ((5 + 3) \times 8)))}{(2 \times ((9 \times (0 + 7)) + 6))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (4 + (5 - (3 - 8))))}{(2 \times (9 - ((0 \times 7) - 6)))} := \frac{(1 + (4 + (5 \times (3 + 8))))}{(1 + (4 + (5 \times (3 + 8))))} := \frac{(1 + (4 + (5 \times 38)))}{((2 - (9 \times (0 - 7))) \times 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (4 + (5 + (3 + 8))))}{(29 - (0 - (7 + 6)))} := \frac{(1 + (4 + (5 + 38)))}{(2 \times (90 - (7 \times 6)))} := \frac{(1 + (4 + (53 + 8)))}{((2 \times (9 \times (0 + 7))) + 6)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (45 - (3 - 8)))}{(2 \times (9 - (0 - (7 \times 6))))} := \frac{(1 + (45 + (3 + 8)))}{(2 \times ((9 \times (0 + 7)) - 6))} := \frac{(1 + (45 + 38))}{(2 + (90 + 76))} \\ &:= \frac{1 + 4538}{2 + 9076} := \frac{14 + 5^3 + 8}{(-2 + 9) \times 07 \times 6} := \frac{14 + 53 + 8}{(2 \times 9 + 07) \times 6} \\ &:= \frac{145 + 38}{290 + 76} := \frac{145 - 38}{290 - 76} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20679}{41358} &:= \frac{((2 - (0 - 6)) \times (7 \times 9))}{(4 \times (1 + ((3^5) + 8)))} := \frac{((2 - (0 - 6)) \times (7 + 9))}{(4 + (1 + ((3^5) + 8)))} := \frac{((2 \times ((0 \times 6) + 7)) + 9)}{(4 - (1 - (3 + (5 \times 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times ((0 \times 6) + 7)) - 9)}{(4 + (1 \times (3 - (5 - 8))))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 \times 6)) + (7 \times 9))}{((41 \times 3) - (5 - 8))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 \times 67)) + 9)}{(4 + ((1^3) + (5 + 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (0 + (6 + 7))) + 9)}{((4 \times (1 \times 3)) + 58)} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + (6 + 7))) - 9)}{(41 - ((3 \times 5) - 8))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + (6 - 7))) + 9)}{(4 + (1 - (3 \times (5 - 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (0 - 6)) + (7 + 9))}{((4 \times (1 - (3 - 5))) - 8)} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + 6)) + 79)}{((41 - 3) \times 5) - 8)} := \frac{((2 \times (0 - 6)) + (7 \times 9))}{(41 + (3 + 58))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (0 - 6)) + (7 + 9))}{((4 - (1 - (3 - 5))) \times 8)} := \frac{((2^{06}) - (7 + 9))}{(4 \times ((1 - (3 - 5)) \times 8))} := \frac{((2^{06}) + (7 \times 9))}{(4 - (1 - ((3^5) + 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^{06}) + (7 + 9))}{(4 \times (1 + (3 \times (5 + 8))))} := \frac{((2^{06}) + (7 - 9))}{(4 + (1 \times (3 \times (5 \times 8))))} := \frac{((20 \times 6) - (7 + 9))}{(4 \times ((1 + 3) \times (5 + 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((20 \times 6) - (7 - 9))}{(4 \times (1 \times (3 + 58)))} := \frac{((20 \times 6) + (7 - 9))}{(4 \times ((1^3) + 58))} := \frac{((20 + 6) \times (7 + 9))}{((4 \times (1 \times 3)) \times (5 + 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{((20 + 67) \times 9)}{(((4 - 1)^3) \times 58)} := \frac{((20 - 6) \times (7 + 9))}{((41 + (3 \times 5)) \times 8)} := \frac{(2 - ((0 - (6 - 7))^9))}{(4 + ((1^3) + (5 - 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - ((0 \times 67) - 9))}{(4 - (((1 - 3) \times 5) - 8))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - ((6 + 7) \times 9)))}{(4 - (1 - ((3^5) - 8)))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (6 - (7 - 9))))}{(4 + (1 \times (3 + (5 + 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (6 + (7 - 9))))}{(4 - (1 + (3 \times (5 - 8))))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (6 + 79)))}{((4 - (1^3)) \times 58)} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (67 + 9)))}{(4 \times (1 \times (3 \times (5 + 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (67 - 9)))}{((4 - (1^3)) \times (5 \times 8))} := \frac{(2 - (0 \times (6 - 79)))}{4 \times 1^{358}} := \frac{(2 - (0 - 679))}{(4 + 1358)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((0 \times 6) + (7 \times 9)))}{((4 \times (13 \times 5)) - 8)} := \frac{(2 \times ((0 \times 6) + (7 + 9)))}{(4 - (1 - (3 + 58)))} := \frac{(2 \times ((0 \times 67) + 9))}{(4 \times ((1^{35}) + 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 - (6 - (7 \times 9))))}{(4 \times ((13 \times 5) - 8))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 - (6 - (7 + 9))))}{(4 \times (1 - (3 \times (5 - 8))))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 - (6 \times (7 - 9))))}{(4 + (1 + (3 + (5 \times 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 - (6 - 79)))}{(4 + ((1 + 35) \times 8))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + ((6 \times 7) - 9)))}{((4 \times (1 \times 35)) - 8)} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (6 - (7 - 9))))}{(4 + (1 + (35 - 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (6 + (7 \times 9))))}{(4 - ((1 - 35) \times 8))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (6 + (7 + 9))))}{((4 - (1 - (3 + 5))) \times 8)} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (6 + (7 - 9))))}{((4 + (1 \times (3 - 5))) \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (67 + 9)))}{((4 - (1 - 35)) \times 8)} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (67 - 9)))}{(4 \times ((1^3) \times 58))} := \frac{2^{0 \times 67 + 9}}{(((41 \times 3) + 5) \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{2^{06-7+9}}{((4 \times (1 - (3 - 5))) \times 8)} := \frac{(2 + ((0 - (6 - 7))^9))}{(4 - ((1^3) + (5 - 8)))} := \frac{(2 + (0 - (6 - (7 + 9))))}{(4 \times (1 \times (3 - (5 - 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (0 - (6 \times (7 - 9))))}{(4 \times (1 + (3 - (5 - 8))))} := \frac{(20 - ((6 - 7) \times 9))}{(4 - (1 + (3 - 58)))} := \frac{(20 - (6 - (7 + 9)))}{(4 + (1 - (3 - 58)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(20 \times (6 - (7 - 9)))}{((4 + (1 + 35)) \times 8)} := \frac{(20 + (6 + (7 \times 9)))}{(4 + (1 \times (3 \times 58)))} := \frac{(20 + (6 + (7 + 9)))}{(4 - ((1 - 3) \times (5 \times 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(20 + (67 + 9))}{(4 \times (((1^3) + 5) \times 8))} := \frac{206 - 7 + 9}{413 - 5 + 8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{26907}{53814} &:= \frac{(((2^6) - (9 - 0)) \times 7)}{(5 \times ((3 + 8) \times 14))} := \frac{(((2^6) \times (9 - 0)) + 7)}{(53 \times (8 + 14))} := \frac{(((2^6) + 90) \times 7)}{((538 + 1) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((2 + 6) \times (9 - 0)) - 7)}{(53 + (81 - 4))} := \frac{((2 - (6 - (9 - 0))) \times 7)}{(5 \times (3 + (8 - (1 - 4))))} := \frac{((2 \times (6 - (9 - 0))) + 7)}{(5 + (3 + (8 - 14)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (6 \times (9 - 0))) - 7)}{((5^3) + (81 - 4))} := \frac{((2 \times 6) - (9 - (0 \times 7)))}{(5 - (3 - (8 - (1 \times 4))))} := \frac{((2 \times 6)^{9-07})}{((5 + 3) \times ((8 + 1) \times 4))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((2 \times 6) + (9 - (0 \times 7)))}{(5 - (3 - (8 \times (1 + 4))))} := \frac{((2 \times 6) + (90 - 7))}{(5 \times (38 \times (1^4)))} := \frac{((2^6) - (9 - (0 - 7)))}{((5 + 3) \times (8 + (1 \times 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^6) - (9 + (0 - 7)))}{((5 \times (3 \times (8 \times 1))) + 4)} := \frac{((2^6) \times (9 - (0 - 7)))}{(5 - 3)^{8+1} \times 4} := \frac{((2^6) \times (9 + (0 - 7)))}{(5 - 3)^8 \times 1^4} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^6)^{9-07})}{((5 - 3) \times (8 \times (1 \times 4)))} := \frac{((2^6) + (9 + (0 - 7)))}{((5^3) + (8 - (1^4)))} := \frac{((2^6) + (90 + 7))}{((5 \times 3) + 8) \times 14} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + (6 - 9)) \times (0 - 7))}{(5 + (3 - (8 - 14)))} := \frac{(2 + 6)^{9+0 \times 7}}{((5 - 3)^{8-1})^4} := \frac{(2 - ((6 - (9 - 0)) \times 7))}{(2 - ((6 - (9 - 0)) \times 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (6 - (9 - (0 \times 7))))}{(5 - (3 - (8 - 14)))} := \frac{(2 - (6 - (9 - (0 - 7))))}{((5 \times (3 + (8 - 1))) - 4)} := \frac{(2 - (6 - (90 + 7)))}{((5 \times (38 \times 1)) - 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (6 - (90 - 7)))}{(5 - (3 - (8 \times (1^4))))} := \frac{(2 - (6 \times (9 \times (0 \times 7))))}{(2 - (6 \times (9 \times (0 - 7))))} := \frac{(2 - (6 \times (9 \times (0 - 7))))}{(2 - (6 \times (9 \times (0 - 7))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((5 - 3) \times 81) - 4)}{(2 - (6 + (9 \times (0 - 7))))} := \frac{(5 + (3 - (8 - (1 \times 4))))}{(2 \times ((6 \times (9 - 0)) + 7))} := \frac{(5 \times (38 \times (1 \times 4)))}{(2 \times ((6 \times 90) + 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5^3) - (8 - (1^4)))}{(2 \times ((6 + (9 - 0)) \times 7))} := \frac{(5 + ((3 \times 81) - 4))}{(2 \times ((6 + (9 - 0))^7))} := \frac{(5 + ((3^8 - 1) - 4))}{(2 \times (6 - (9 + (0 - 7))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times (3 \times ((8 - 1) \times 4)))}{(2 \times (6 \times (9 - (0 \times 7))))} := \frac{(((5 \times 3)^{8-1}) \times 4)}{(2 \times (6 \times (9 - (0 - 7))))} := \frac{(5 + (3 + (8 \times (1^4))))}{(2 \times (6 + (9 - (0 \times 7))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((5 \times (3 + 8)) - 1) \times 4)}{(2 \times (6 + (9 - (0 - 7))))} := \frac{(((5 \times 3) + 81) \times 4)}{(2 \times (6 + (90 - 7)))} := \frac{(5 \times (3 + (8 + (1^4))))}{(2 \times (69 + (0 - 7)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 + 3) \times (8 - (1 - 4)))}{2^6 + 9 \times 0 \times 7} := \frac{((5 + (3 + 81)) \times 4)}{2^{6-9+07}} := \frac{(5 + (3^{8+1-4}))}{2^{6+9-07}} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 + (3 \times (8 + 1))) \times 4)}{(2 + ((6 \times (9 - 0)) - 7))} := \frac{(5 + (3 \times (8 + (1^4))))}{(2 + (6 - (9 + (0 - 7))))} := \frac{((5 - 3)^{8+1^4})}{(2 + (6 \times (9 - (0 \times 7))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((5 \times 3) - 8) \times 14)}{(2 + (6 \times (9 + (0 - 7))))} := \frac{(5 + (3 + (8 - (1 \times 4))))}{(2 + (6 \times (90 - 7)))} := \frac{((5 + ((3 \times 8) - 1)) \times 4)}{(2 + (6^{9-07}))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + ((3 \times (8 + 1)) - 4))}{(2 + (6 + (9 - (0 \times 7))))} := \frac{((5^3) \times (8 \times (1^4)))}{(2 + (6 + (9 - (0 - 7))))} := \frac{(((5 + 3) \times (8 + 1)) + 4)}{(2 + (6 + (9 + (0 - 7))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 - (3 - (8 \times (1 \times 4))))}{(2 + (6 + (90 + 7)))} := \frac{(5 + (3 + (8 \times (1 + 4))))}{(26 - (9 \times (0 \times 7)))} := \frac{(5 + (3 \times (8 + (1 - 4))))}{(26 \times (9 - (0 \times 7)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times (38 + (1 \times 4)))}{(26 \times (9 + (0 - 7)))} := \frac{((5 \times (3 + 8)) + (1 - 4))}{(26 + (9 + (0 - 7)))} := \frac{(((5^3) - (8 \times 1)) \times 4)}{(269 - (0 \times 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 + (3 \times (8 - 1))) \times 4)}{269 + 07} := \frac{((5 \times (3 + (8 + 1))) - 4)}{269 - 07} := \frac{(538 \times (1^4))}{538 - 14} \\
 &:= \frac{269 + 07}{538 + 14} := \frac{269 - 07}{538 - 14}
 \end{aligned}$$

► **29073**
58146

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((2 \times (9 - 0)) + 7) \times 3)}{(5 \times ((8 + (1 - 4)) \times 6))} := \frac{(((2 + (9 - 0)) \times 7) + 3)}{(5 \times (8 + (1 \times (4 \times 6))))} := \frac{(((2 - 9) \times (0 - 7)) + 3)}{((5 \times (8 + 14)) - 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 - (9 \times (0 - 7))) \times 3)}{(5 \times ((8 + (1 + 4)) \times 6))} := \frac{((2 \times (9 - (0 - 7))) + 3)}{(5 \times (8 + ((1^4) \times 6)))} := \frac{((2 \times (9 - (0 - 7))) - 3)}{(5 + (8 - (1 - 46)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (9 \times (0 + 7))) + 3)}{(((5 \times 8) - (1 - 4)) \times 6)} := \frac{((2 \times (9 \times (0 + 7))) - 3)}{((5 + ((8 + 1) \times 4)) \times 6)} := \frac{((2 \times (9 - 0)) + (7 \times 3))}{((5 + (8 \times (1^4))) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (9 - 0)) + (7 + 3))}{(58 + (1 \times (4 - 6)))} := \frac{((2 \times (9 - 0)) + (7 - 3))}{(5 - (8 - (1 + 46)))} := \frac{((2 \times (90 - 7)) + 3)}{(((5 + 81) \times 4) - 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times 90) - (7 \times 3))}{((58 - (1 + 4)) \times 6)} := \frac{((2 + (9 - (0 \times 7))) \times 3)}{((5 - (8 - 14)) \times 6)} := \frac{((2 + (9 - (0 - 7))) \times 3)}{((5 + (8 + (1 + 4))) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + (9 - 0)) \times (7 - 3))}{(5 + (81 - (4 - 6)))} := \frac{((2 + 90) \times (7 + 3))}{(5 \times (8 \times (1 \times 46)))} := \frac{((29 - (0 - 7)) \times 3)}{(((5 \times (8 \times 1)) - 4) \times 6)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((2-9) \times (0 - (7 \times 3)))}{(((5 \times (8 + 1)) + 4) \times 6)} := \frac{((2-9) \times (0 - (7 + 3)))}{(5 \times (8 + (14 + 6)))} := \frac{(2 - ((9 \times (0 \times 7)) - 3))}{(5 + (8 - (1 - (4 - 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - ((9 \times (0 - 7)) + 3))}{((5 \times 8) + (14 \times 6))} := \frac{(2 - (9 \times (0 - (7 - 3))))}{(5 + (81 - (4 + 6)))} := \frac{(2 - (9 \times (0 \times 73)))}{(5 + (8 + (1 - (4 + 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (9 + (0 - (7 \times 3))))}{(58 - ((1 + 4) \times 6))} := \frac{(2 - (9 + (0 - (7 + 3))))}{(5 - (8 + (1 - (4 + 6))))} := \frac{(2 - (9 + (0 - 73)))}{(5 + (81 + 46))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((9 \times (0 \times 7)) + 3))}{(5 + (8 + (1 + (4 - 6))))} := \frac{(2 \times ((9 \times (0 + 7)) + 3))}{(((5 \times (8 \times 1)) + 4) \times 6)} := \frac{(2 \times ((9 \times (0 + 7)) - 3))}{(5 \times (8 \times ((1^4) \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((9 + (0 - 7)) \times 3))}{(2 \times ((9 + (0 - 7)) \times 3))} := \frac{(2 \times ((9 + (0 - 7))^3))}{(2 \times ((9 \times (0 + 7)) - 3))} := \frac{(2 \times (9 - ((0 \times 7) - 3)))}{(2 \times (9 - ((0 \times 7) - 3)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (9 - (0 - (7 \times 3))))}{(5 + (8 + (1 + (4 + 6))))} := \frac{(2 \times (9 - (0 - (7 - 3))))}{((5 \times 8) - (14 - 6))} := \frac{(2 \times (9 - (0 \times 73)))}{((5 + (8 - (1 + 4))) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times (8 \times (1 - (4 - 6))))}{(2 \times (9 \times (0 + (7 + 3))))} := \frac{(58 - ((1^4) \times 6))}{(2 \times (9 + (0 - (7 - 3))))} := \frac{(5 + (8 - (1 - (4 \times 6))))}{(2 \times (90 - (7 + 3)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (9 \times (0 + (7 + 3))))}{(5 \times ((8 + (1 \times 4)) \times 6))} := \frac{(5 - (8 + (1 - (4 \times 6))))}{(2 \times (90 - 73))} := \frac{(5 \times (8 \times (14 - 6)))}{2^{9-07+3}} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (90 + (7 + 3)))}{(5 \times (8 \times (1 \times (4 + 6))))} := \frac{(58 + (1 \times (4 + 6)))}{(2 + ((9 + (0 - 7)) \times 3))} := \frac{((5 - (8 - (1 + 4)))^6)}{(2 + (9 - (0 - (7 - 3))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + ((9 + (0 - 7)) \times 3))}{(5 + (8 + (1 - (4 - 6))))} := \frac{(5 - (8 + (1 - 46)))}{(2 + (9 + (0 - (7 + 3))))} := \frac{(5 \times (8 + (1 \times (4 - 6))))}{(2 + (9 + (0 - (7 - 3))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (9 - (0 \times 73)))}{(5 + (8 - (1 - (4 + 6))))} := \frac{(2 + (9 + (0 - (7 + 3))))}{(5 + (8 - (1 + (4 + 6))))} := \frac{(5 + (8 - (1 + (4 - 6))))}{(2 + (90 + (7 \times 3)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (90 - (7 \times 3)))}{(58 + (14 \times 6))} := \frac{(2 + (90 - (7 - 3)))}{(((5 + 8) \times 14) - 6)} := \frac{(2 + (90 + (7 \times 3)))}{((58 \times (1 \times 4)) - 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(58 + (14 \times 6))}{(2 + (90 + (7 + 3)))} := \frac{((5 + 8) \times 14 - 6)}{(2 + (90 + 73))} := \frac{((58 \times (1 \times 4)) - 6)}{(2 + (90 - 73))} \\
 &:= \frac{(58 + 146)}{(29 \times ((0 \times 7) + 3))} := \frac{(5 \times ((8 - (1 - 4)) \times 6))}{(29 \times (0 + (7 + 3)))} := \frac{(5 + (8 + (1 + (4 \times 6))))}{(29 + (0 - (7 - 3)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(29 \times ((0 \times 7) + 3))}{((5 - (8 \times (1 - 4))) \times 6)} := \frac{(58 \times (1 \times (4 + 6)))}{(5 \times (8 - (1 \times (4 - 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{2907 + 3}{5814 + 6} := \frac{2907 - 3}{5814 - 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.58 60 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{27069}{54138} &:= \frac{(((2 \times (7 - 0)) + 6) \times 9)}{(5 \times ((4 \times (1 \times 3)) + 8))} := \frac{(((2 \times (7 - 0)) - 6) \times 9)}{(((5 \times (4 - 1)) + 3) \times 8)} := \frac{(((2 - 7) \times (0 - 6)) + 9)}{(54 + (1 \times (3 \times 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((2 - 7) \times (0 - 6)) - 9)}{(54 - (1 + (3 + 8)))} := \frac{((2 - (7 - 0)) \times (6 - 9))}{(5 + (4 + (13 + 8)))} := \frac{((2 \times (7 - (0 \times 6))) - 9)}{(5 + (4 + ((1^3)^8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (7 - (0 - 6))) + 9)}{(5 \times (4 - (1 - (3 + 8))))} := \frac{((2 \times (7 - (0 - 6))) - 9)}{(5 + (4 + (1 + (3 \times 8))))} := \frac{((2 \times (7 \times (0 + 6))) - 9)}{(5 \times (41 - (3 + 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (7 - 0)) + (6 \times 9))}{((5 + (4 \times (1 \times 3))) \times 8)} := \frac{((2 \times (7 - 0)) + (6 + 9))}{((5 \times (4 \times 1)) + 38)} := \frac{((2 + (7 - (0 - 6))) \times 9)}{(54 \times (13 - 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{54^{138}}{((2 + (7 + (0 - 6))) \times 9)} := \frac{((2 + (7 - 0)) \times 69)}{((5 + 4) \times 138)} := \frac{((27 - (0 - 6)) \times 9)}{(54 \times (1 \times (3 + 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 - 7) \times (0 - (6 \times 9)))}{(5 \times (4 + (13 \times 8)))} := \frac{((27 \times (0 + 6)) + 9)}{((5 + (4 \times 1)) \times 38)} := \frac{((2 - 70) \times (6 - 9))}{((54 - (1 \times 3)) \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{((270 + 6) \times 9)}{(((5^4) - (1 + 3)) \times 8)} := \frac{(2 - ((7 + (0 - 6))^9))}{(5 - (4 - ((1^3)^8)))} := \frac{(2 - (7 \times ((0 \times 6) - 9)))}{(((5 + 41) \times 3) - 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (7 \times (0 - (6 \times 9))))}{(5 \times (4 \times (1 \times 38)))} := \frac{(2 - (7 \times (0 \times 69)))}{(5 + (4 + (1 \times (3 - 8))))} := \frac{(2 - (7 + ((0 \times 6) - 9)))}{(5 + (4 - ((1^3)^8)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(2 - (7 + (0 - (6 + 9))))}{(5 + (4 + (1 \times (3 + 8))))} := \frac{(2 - (7 + (0 - 69)))}{(((5 \times 4) - (1 + 3)) \times 8)} := \frac{(2 - (70 \times (6 - 9)))}{((54 - (1^3)) \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((7 + (0 - 6)) \times 9))}{((5 \times (4 + 1)) + (3 + 8))} := \frac{(2 \times ((70 - 6)^9))}{((5 + (41 \times 3))^8)} := \frac{(2 \times (7 - ((0 \times 6) - 9)))}{((5 + (4 - (1^3))) \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (7 - (0 - (6 + 9))))}{((5 + (4 - (1 - 3))) \times 8)} := \frac{(2 \times (7 - (0 - (6 - 9))))}{(5 + (4 - ((1^3) - 8)))} := \frac{(2 \times (7 - (0 \times 69)))}{((5 \times (4 \times (1^3))) + 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (7 - (0 - 69)))}{((5 + (4 - 1)) \times 38)} := \frac{(2 \times (7 \times ((0 \times 6) + 9)))}{((5 \times (4 \times 13)) - 8)} := \frac{(2 \times (7 \times (0 - (6 - 9))))}{(5 + (41 + 38))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (7 \times (0 + (6 + 9))))}{(5 \times (4 \times (13 + 8)))} := \frac{(2 \times (7 + (0 - (6 - 9))))}{(5 - (4 - (1 + 38)))} := \frac{(2 \times (70 - (6 + 9)))}{(5 \times (4 \times (1 \times (3 + 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (70 + (6 - 9)))}{((5 \times (4 \times 13)) + 8)} := \frac{2^{(7-06) \times 9}}{((5 + (41 \times 3)) \times 8)} := \frac{2^{7+06-9}}{(5 + (4 - (1 - (3 \times 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{2^7 + 0 \times 69}{((5 - (4 - (1^3)))^8)} := \frac{(2 + ((7 + (0 - 6)) \times 9))}{(5 - (4 - (13 + 8)))} := \frac{(2 + ((7 + (0 - 6))^9))}{(5 - (4 + (1 \times (3 - 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (7 - (0 - (6 + 9))))}{(5 + (4 + (1 + 38)))} := \frac{(2 + (7 - (0 - (6 - 9))))}{(5 - (4 - (1 \times (3 + 8))))} := \frac{(2 + (7 - (0 \times 69)))}{(5 + (4 + ((1^3) + 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (7 \times (0 - (6 - 9))))}{(5 + (4 - (1 - 38)))} := \frac{(2 + (7 + (0 - (6 - 9))))}{(5 - (4 + (1 - (3 \times 8))))} := \frac{(2 + (70 - (6 + 9)))}{((5^4-1) - (3 + 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (70 + (6 - 9)))}{(5 + (((4 + 1)^3) + 8))} := \frac{(27 - ((0 \times 6) - 9))}{((5 + (4 \times (1^3))) \times 8)} := \frac{(27 - (0 - 69))}{((5 + (4 - 1)) \times (3 \times 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(27 \times ((0 \times 6) + 9))}{(54 \times ((1^3) + 8))} := \frac{(27 + (0 - (6 - 9)))}{(5 \times (4 + ((1^3) \times 8)))} := \frac{(270 - (6 \times 9))}{(54 \times ((1^3) \times 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(270 - (6 - 9))}{(541 - (3 - 8))} := \frac{(270 + (6 \times 9))}{(54 \times (1 + (3 + 8)))} := \frac{(270 + (6 + 9))}{(5 \times ((4 - 1) \times 38))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► **46851**
93702

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((4 + (6 - 8)) \times 5) - 1)}{(9 \times 3) - (7 - (0 - 2))} := \frac{(((4 + 68) \times 5) + 1)}{((9^3) - (7 - (0 \times 2)))} := \frac{(((46 - 8) \times 5) - 1)}{(9 \times (3 \times (7 \times (0 + 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times ((6 \times 8) + 5)) - 1)}{((9 - 3) \times 70) + 2} := \frac{((4 \times (6 \times (8 - 5))) + 1)}{(9 - (3 - (70 \times 2)))} := \frac{((4 \times (6 \times (8 - 5))) - 1)}{(93 + (7^{02}))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times (6 + (8 - 5))) + 1)}{(9 - (3 - (70 - 2)))} := \frac{((4 \times (6 + 8)) - 51)}{((9 + (3 - (7 - 0))) \times 2)} := \frac{((4 \times (6 - 8)) + 51)}{(93 - (7 - (0 \times 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times 6) + (8 - (5 \times 1)))}{((9 - 3) \times (7 - (0 - 2)))} := \frac{((4 + (6 + 8)) \times (5 \times 1))}{(9 \times ((3 + (7 - 0)) \times 2))} := \frac{((4 + (6 + 8)) \times 51)}{(9 \times (3 \times (70 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 + 6) \times (8 - (5 + 1)))}{(((9 - 3) \times (7 - 0)) - 2)} := \frac{((4 + 6) \times (85 - 1))}{((9 + 3) \times (70 \times 2))} := \frac{(4 + 6)^{8-5-1}}{((93 + (7 - 0)) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 + 68) \times (5 + 1))}{((9 + 3) \times (70 + 2))} := \frac{((46 \times 8) - (5 + 1))}{((9^3) - (7 + (0 - 2)))} := \frac{((46 \times 8) + 51)}{(((9 + 3) \times 70) - 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (((6 - 8) \times 5) - 1))}{(9 + (3 \times (7 - (0 \times 2))))} := \frac{(4 - (6 - ((8 \times 5) + 1)))}{(9 - (3 - (70 + 2)))} := \frac{(4 - (6 - (8 - (5 \times 1))))}{((9 - (3 + 7)) \times (0 - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (6 - (8 \times (5 \times 1))))}{((9 \times 3) + (7^{02}))} := \frac{(4 - (6 - (8 \times (5 + 1))))}{((9 \times (3 + (7 - 0))) + 2)} := \frac{(4 - (6 - (8 \times (5 - 1))))}{((9 + (3 \times (7 - 0))) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (6 - (8 + (5 \times 1))))}{((9 \times 3) - (7 + (0 - 2)))} := \frac{(4 - (6 - (8 + (5 - 1))))}{(9 - (3 + (7 \times (0 - 2))))} := \frac{(4 - (6 - (85 + 1)))}{((9 + 3) \times (7 \times (0 + 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (6 + (8 - 51)))}{(((9 + 3) \times (7 - 0)) - 2)} := \frac{(4 \times (6 - (8 - (5 \times 1))))}{(9 + (3 \times (7 + (0 - 2))))} := \frac{(4 \times (6 \times ((8 \times 5) - 1)))}{(9 \times ((3 \times 70) - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 + (8 - (5 \times 1))))}{(9 \times (3 + (7 + (0 - 2))))} := \frac{(4 \times (6 + (8 - (5 - 1))))}{(9 + (3 + (70 - 2)))} := \frac{(4 \times (6 + (8 \times (5 + 1))))}{((9 - 3) \times (70 + 2))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 + (8 \times 51)))}{(9 \times (370 - 2))} &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 + (8 + (5 \times 1))))}{(9 + (3 + (70 \times 2)))} &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 + (85 + 1)))}{((9^3) + (7 - (0 \times 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (6 + (85 - 1)))}{((9^3) - (7 - (0 - 2)))} &:= \frac{4^{6-8+5-1}}{(9 + ((3 \times (7 - 0)) + 2))} &:= \frac{(4 + ((6 \times (8 - 5)) - 1))}{((9 - 3) \times (7 - (0 \times 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + ((6^{8-5}) - 1))}{((9 + (3 \times 70)) \times 2)} &:= \frac{(4 + (6 - (8 - (5 - 1))))}{(9 + (3 - (7 \times (0 \times 2))))} &:= \frac{(4 + (6 \times (8 - (5 \times 1))))}{(9 + (37 + (0 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (6 \times (8 - (5 - 1))))}{((9 - 37) \times (0 - 2))} &:= \frac{(4 + (6 \times (8 + (5 \times 1))))}{((9 + (3 + 70)) \times 2)} &:= \frac{(4 + (6 + ((8 \times 5) + 1)))}{(93 + (7 - (0 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (6 + ((8 \times 5) - 1)))}{(93 + (7 + (0 - 2)))} &:= \frac{(4 + (6 + (8 - (5 \times 1))))}{(9 + (3 - (7 \times (0 - 2))))} &:= \frac{(4 + (6 + (8 - (5 - 1))))}{(9 + ((3 \times (7 - 0)) - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (6 + (8 \times (5 \times 1))))}{(93 + (7 - (0 \times 2)))} &:= \frac{(4 + (6 + (8 \times (5 - 1))))}{(9 + (3 + (70 + 2)))} &:= \frac{(4 + (6 + (8 + (5 \times 1))))}{(9 + (37 - (0 \times 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (6 + (8 + (5 + 1))))}{(9 + (37 - (0 - 2)))} &:= \frac{(4 + (68 + (5 + 1)))}{(9 + (3 \times (7^{02})))} &:= \frac{(4 + (685 \times 1))}{(9 + (37^{02}))} \\
 &:= \frac{(46 - (8 - (5 + 1)))}{((9 \times (3 + (7 - 0))) - 2)} &:= \frac{(46 - (8 + (5 - 1)))}{(((9 \times 3) + (7 - 0)) \times 2)} &:= \frac{(46 + (8 \times (5 \times 1)))}{((93 - (7 - 0)) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(46 + (8 - 51))}{(9 - (3 - (7 \times (0 \times 2))))} &:= \frac{4685 + 1}{9370 + 2} &:= \frac{4685 - 1}{9370 - 2}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.59 61 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{14853}{29706} &:= \frac{(((1 + 4)^{8-5}) + 3)}{(2^{9-7+06})} &:= \frac{((1 - (4 - (8 + 5))) \times 3)}{((2 \times 9) - (7 \times (0 - 6)))} &:= \frac{((1 - (4 - 8)) \times (5 \times 3))}{(((2 \times 9) + (7 - 0)) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{1^4 \times 8^{5+3}}{(2 \times ((9 + (7 - 0))^6))} &:= \frac{((1 + ((4 + 8) \times 5)) \times 3)}{((2 - (9 \times 7)) \times (0 - 6))} &:= \frac{((1 + (4 - (8 - 5)))^3)}{(2 \times (9 - (7 + (0 - 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (4 \times (8 \times 5))) \times 3)}{(2 + (970 - 6))} &:= \frac{((1 + (4 \times 8)) \times (5 + 3))}{(((2 \times 9) + 70) \times 6)} &:= \frac{((1 + (4^{8-5})) \times 3)}{((2 + (9 \times (7 - 0))) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{((1 + (4 + (8 + 5))) \times 3)}{((2 + (9 + (7 - 0))) \times 6)} &:= \frac{((14 + 85) \times 3)}{((2 + (97 - 0)) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(1 - (((4 - 8) \times 5) + 3))}{(29 + (7 - (0 \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - ((4 \times 8) - (5^3)))}{((2 \times (97 - 0)) - 6)} &:= \frac{(1 - (4 - ((8 - 5) \times 3)))}{(2 + (9 + (7 + (0 - 6))))} &:= \frac{(1 - (4 - (8 - (5 - 3))))}{(2 - (9 - (7 - (0 - 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (4 - (8 \times (5 \times 3))))}{(2 \times (9 \times (7 - (0 - 6))))} &:= \frac{(1 - (4 - (8 \times (5 - 3))))}{((2 \times (9 + (7 - 0))) - 6)} &:= \frac{(1 - (4 - (8 + (5 - 3))))}{(2 + ((9 - (7 - 0)) \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (4 - (85 + 3)))}{(2 \times (9 + (70 + 6)))} &:= \frac{(1 - (4 + (8 - 53)))}{((2 - (9 + 7)) \times (0 - 6))} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((4 \times (8 - 5)) - 3))}{2 \times 9^{7-06}} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((4 \times 85) + 3))}{(2 + (9 \times (70 + 6)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((4 + (8 + 5)) \times 3))}{(2 \times (9 - (7 \times (0 - 6))))} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((4 + 8) \times 53))}{(2 \times ((9 \times 70) + 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((48 \times 5) + 3))}{((2 + (9 + 70)) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 - (8 - 53)))}{(2 + ((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 6))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 \times ((8 - 5)^3)))}{((29 + (7 - 0)) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 \times (8 \times (5 - 3))))}{(2 \times ((9 - (7 - 0))^6))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 \times (8^{5-3})))}{2^9 \times (7 - 06)} &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 \times (85 + 3)))}{((2 + 9) \times (70 - 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 + ((8 \times 5) + 3)))}{((2 \times 9) + (70 + 6))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 + (8 - (5 - 3))))}{(2 \times (9 + (7 + (0 - 6))))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (4 + (8 + (5 - 3))))}{(29 - (7 + (0 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (48 - (5 \times 3)))}{(2 + ((9 - (7 - 0))^6))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (48 - (5 - 3)))}{((2^9) - (70 \times 6))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (48 \times (5 - 3)))}{(2 \times ((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 6))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (48 + (5 \times 3)))}{(2 \times (9 \times (7 - (0 \times 6))))} := \frac{1^{4853}}{(2 - (9 \times (7 \times (0 \times 6))))} := \frac{(1 + (((4 \times 8) - 5) \times 3))}{((2 \times (9 + 70)) + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + ((4 - (8 - 5))^3))}{2^{9-7+0 \times 6}} := \frac{(1 + ((4 \times (8 - 5)) + 3))}{(2 \times (9 + (7 - (0 \times 6))))} := \frac{(1 + ((4 + (8 - 5)) \times 3))}{(2 \times (9 + (7 - (0 - 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + ((48 \times 5) - 3))}{(2 + ((9 + 70) \times 6))} := \frac{(1 + (4 - (8 - (5 \times 3))))}{(2 + (9 + (7 - (0 - 6))))} := \frac{(1 + (4 - (8 - (5 + 3))))}{(2 + (9 - (7 + (0 - 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (4 \times (8 + (5 - 3))))}{((2 \times 9) + (70 - 6))} := \frac{(1 + (4 + (8 - (5 - 3))))}{(29 - (7 - (0 \times 6)))} := \frac{(1 + (4 + (8 \times (5 - 3))))}{(29 + (7 - (0 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (4 + (8 \times 53)))}{(2 \times (9 + (70 \times 6)))} := \frac{(1 + (4 + (8^{5-3})))}{(2 \times ((9 \times (7 - 0)) + 6))} := \frac{(1 + (4 + (8 + (5 - 3))))}{(29 + (7 + (0 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (4 + (8 + 53)))}{((2 \times (9 \times (7 - 0))) + 6)} := \frac{(1 + (48 \times (5 - 3)))}{(2 \times (97 - (0 \times 6)))} := \frac{(1 + (48 + (5 + 3)))}{(2 \times ((9 \times (7 - 0)) - 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (485 + 3))}{(2 + (970 + 6))} := \frac{(1 + 4853)}{(2 + 9706)} := \frac{(14 \times ((8 - 5)^3))}{(2 \times (9 \times (7 \times (0 + 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(14 \times (8 \times (5 - 3)))}{((2^9) - (70 - 6))} := \frac{(14 + (8 + (5^3)))}{((2 - 9) \times (7 \times (0 - 6)))} := \frac{1485 + 3}{2970 + 6} \\
 &:= \frac{1485 - 3}{2970 - 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

► **20394**
81576

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((2 - (0 - 3)) \times 9) + 4)}{(8 \times 15) + 76} := \frac{(((2 \times (0 - 3)) + 9)^4)}{(81 \times (5 - (7 - 6)))} := \frac{(((2^{03}) \times 9) + 4)}{(8 \times (1 - (5 - (7 \times 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((20 \times 3) - 9) \times 4)}{(815 + (7 - 6))} := \frac{(((20 - 3) \times 9) - 4)}{((81 + 5) \times 7) - 6} := \frac{((2 - (0 - (3 \times 9))) \times 4)}{(8 + ((1 + 5) \times 76))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 - (0 - (3 + 9))) \times 4)}{(8 + ((1 + (5 \times 7)) \times 6))} := \frac{((2 - (0 - 3)) \times (9 + 4))}{(8 + ((1 + 5) \times (7 \times 6)))} := \frac{((2 - (0 - 39)) \times 4)}{(8 \times (1 + (5 + 76)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times ((0 \times 3) + 9)) + 4)}{(8 - (1 - (5 + 76)))} := \frac{((2 \times ((0 \times 3) + 9)) - 4)}{(8 \times (1 + (5 + (7 - 6))))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 \times 3)) + (9 \times 4))}{(8 \times (1 \times (5 + (7 + 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (0 \times 3)) + (9 - 4))}{(8 - (1 \times ((5 - 7) \times 6)))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 \times 3)) + 94)}{(8 \times (1 \times (5 + (7 \times 6))))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + (3 \times 9))) + 4)}{(8 \times (1 \times ((5 \times 7) - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (0 + (3 + 9))) + 4)}{(8 \times (15 - (7 - 6)))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + 3)) - (9 - 4))}{(8 + (1 - (5 \times (7 - 6))))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + 3)) + (9 \times 4))}{((8 + (1 - 5)) \times (7 \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (0 + 3)) + (9 + 4))}{(81 - (5 \times (7 - 6)))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + 3)) + (9 - 4))}{(8 - (1 + (5 - (7 \times 6))))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + 39)) + 4)}{(8 \times (1 \times ((5 \times 7) + 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (0 - 3)) + (9 + 4))}{((8 - 1) \times (5 - (7 - 6)))} := \frac{2^{-03+9} - 4}{(8 \times (1 + ((5 \times 7) - 6)))} := \frac{((2^{03}) - (9 - 4))}{(8 - (1 - (5 \times (7 - 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^{03}) \times (9 + 4))}{(8 \times (1 + (57 - 6)))} := \frac{((2^{03}) + (9 \times 4))}{(8 - ((1 - 5) \times (7 \times 6)))} := \frac{((2^{03}) + (9 + 4))}{(8 + ((1^5) \times 76))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^{03}) + (9 - 4))}{((8 + (1 - 5)) \times (7 + 6))} := \frac{((2^{03}) + 94)}{(8 \times (1 \times (57 - 6)))} := \frac{((20 \times 3) - (9 \times 4))}{((8 + (15 - 7)) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{((20 \times 3) + 94)}{(8 \times ((1^5) + 76))} := \frac{(2 - ((0 \times 3) - (9 \times 4)))}{(8 \times (1 + (5 + (7 + 6))))} := \frac{(2 - ((0 \times 3) - (9 + 4)))}{(8 + (1 + (57 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - ((0 \times 39) - 4))}{(8 + (15 + (7 - 6)))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - ((3 \times 9) + 4)))}{(81 + (57 - 6))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (3 + (9 + 4))))}{(8 \times (1 - (5 - (7 + 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (3 + (9 - 4))))}{(8 \times (1 \times (5 \times (7 - 6))))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (3 + 94)))}{((8 + (1 + 57)) \times 6)} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (39 + 4)))}{((8 + (15 + 7)) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (0 \times (3 - 94)))}{(8 \times (1^{576}))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - 394))}{(8 + 1576)} := \frac{(2 \times ((0 \times 3) + (9 \times 4)))}{(8 \times (((1 + 5) \times 7) - 6))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((0 \times 39) + 4))}{(8 \times (1 \times (5 - (7 - 6))))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 - (3 - (9 \times 4))))}{((8 + (1 + (5 \times 7))) \times 6)} := \frac{(2 \times (0 - (3 - (9 + 4))))}{(8 + (1 - (5 - 76)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 - (3 - 94)))}{(8 \times (15 + 76))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + ((3 + 9) \times 4))}{(8 \times (1 + (5 + (7 \times 6))))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (3 \times (9 + 4))))}{(8 - ((1 - 5) \times 76))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (3 \times (9 - 4))))}{((8 + (1 \times (5 + 7))) \times 6)} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (3 + (9 + 4))))}{(8 \times (15 + (7 - 6)))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (3 + (9 - 4))))}{(8 \times (15 - (7 + 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (39 + 4)))}{(8 - ((1 - 57) \times 6))} := \frac{2^{-03+9-4}}{(8 - (1 \times (5 - (7 + 6))))} := \frac{(2 + (0 - ((3 - 9) \times 4)))}{(8 \times (1 - ((5 - 7) \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (0 - (3 - (9 \times 4))))}{(8 + ((15 + 7) \times 6))} := \frac{(2 + (0 - (3 - (9 + 4))))}{(8 \times (1 + (5 \times (7 - 6))))} := \frac{(20 - (3 - (9 \times 4)))}{(8 - ((1 - (5 \times 7)) \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(20 + (3 \times (9 \times 4)))}{(8 \times (1 + (57 + 6)))} := \frac{(20 + (3 \times 94))}{(8 \times (157 - 6))} := \frac{(20 + (39 + 4))}{((8 - (1 - (5 \times 7))) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(203 - (9 - 4))}{(8 \times ((15 \times 7) - 6))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► **20769**
41538

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((2 - (0 - 7)) \times 6) - 9)}{((41 \times (5 - 3)) + 8)} := \frac{(((2 \times (0 + 7)) + 6) \times 9)}{((4 - 1) \times (5 \times (3 \times 8)))} := \frac{(((2 \times (0 + 7)) - 6) \times 9)}{((4 - (1 - (5 \times 3))) \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times ((0 \times 7) + 6)) + 9)}{(4 + ((1^5) \times 38))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 - (7 - 6))) + 9)}{(4 + (1 \times (5 - (3 - 8))))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 \times 76)) + 9)}{(41 - ((5 \times 3) + 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (0 + (7 + 6))) + 9)}{(4 + ((1 + 5) \times (3 + 8)))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + (7 + 6))) - 9)}{(4 + (1 + (5 + (3 \times 8))))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + 7)) + (6 \times 9))}{(4 \times (1 - (5 - 38)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (0 + 7)) + (6 + 9))}{(4 - (1 - (5 \times (3 + 8))))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 - 7)) + (6 \times 9))}{(4 \times (1 - (5 - (3 \times 8))))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 - 7)) + 69)}{((4 + (1 + 5)) \times (3 + 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^{0 \times 7 + 6}) + 9)}{(((41 + 5) \times 3) + 8)} := \frac{((2^{07}) - (6 \times 9))}{(4 + ((15 + 3) \times 8))} := \frac{((2^{07}) + (6 \times 9))}{(4 + (15 \times (3 \times 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + (0 - 7)) \times (6 - 9))}{(4 + (1 - (5 \times (3 - 8))))} := \frac{((20 - (7 - 6)) \times 9)}{((4 + (1 \times 5)) \times 38)} := \frac{((20 \times 7) - (6 \times 9))}{(4 \times (1 \times (5 + 38)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((20 + 76) \times 9)}{(4 \times ((1 + 53) \times 8))} := \frac{(2 - ((0 \times 76) - 9))}{(4 - (1 + (5 - (3 \times 8))))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - ((7 + 6) \times 9)))}{(((4 - 1)^5) + (3 - 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (7 - (6 - 9))))}{(4 + (1 - (5 - (3 \times 8))))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (7 \times (6 \times 9))))}{(4 \times (1 \times (5 \times 38)))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (7 + (6 + 9))))}{(4 + (1 + (5 + 38)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (7 + (6 - 9))))}{(4 + ((1^{53}) \times 8))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (7 + 69)))}{(4 \times (15 + (3 \times 8)))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - (76 + 9)))}{(41 + ((5^3) + 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (1 + ((5^3) + 8)))}{(2 \times ((0 \times 7) + (6 \times 9)))} := \frac{(4 \times (1 - (5 + (3 - 8))))}{(2 \times ((0 \times 7) + (6 + 9)))} := \frac{(4 + 1538)}{(2 \times ((0 \times 76) + 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((4 - (1^5))^3) \times 8)}{(4 \times (15 \times 3)) + 8)} := \frac{(4 + (1 + (5 \times (3 + 8))))}{((4 \times 15) + (3 \times 8))} := \frac{(4 - (1 + (5 - 38)))}{(4 \times (1 + (53 + 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 - (7 - (6 \times 9))))}{(2 \times (0 + ((7 \times 6) + 9)))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 - (7 \times (6 - 9))))}{(2 \times (0 + ((7 \times 6) - 9)))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 - (7 - 69)))}{(2 \times (0 + ((7 + 6) \times 9)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times (1 \times 53)) - 8)}{(4 \times (1 \times (5 - (3 - 8))))} := \frac{(4 + ((1 + (5 \times 3)) \times 8))}{(4 - ((1 - 53) \times 8))} := \frac{(4 \times (1 \times ((5^3) - 8)))}{(4 \times (1 \times (53 + 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (7 - (6 - 9))))}{(2 \times (0 + (7 + (6 + 9))))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (7 \times (6 + 9))))}{(2 \times (0 + (7 + (6 - 9))))} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (7 + (6 \times 9))))}{(2 \times (0 + (7 + 69)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (7 + (6 + 9))))}{((4 - (1 - (5 + 3))) \times 8)} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (7 + (6 - 9))))}{((4 - (1 \times (5 - 3))) \times 8)} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (7 + 69)))}{((4 - (1 - 5)) \times 38)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (7 + (6 + 9))))}{2^{0 \times 76 + 9}} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (7 + (6 - 9))))}{2^{-07 + 6 + 9}} := \frac{(2 \times (0 + (7 + 69)))}{(2^{07 + 6 - 9})} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 - (1 - (5^3))) \times 8)}{((4 \times (1 + (5^3))) + 8)} := \frac{((4 - (1 - (5 + (3 \times 8))))}{(4 - (1 - (5 + (3 \times 8))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(2 + ((0 \times 7) - (6 - 9)))}{(4 - (1 \times (5 - (3 + 8))))} := \frac{(2 + (0 - ((7 - 6)^9))}{(((4 - (1 + 5)) \times 3) + 8)} := \frac{(2 + (0 - (7 - (6 \times 9))))}{((4 \times 15) + 38)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (0 - (7 - (6 + 9))))}{(4 + (1 \times (5 + (3 + 8))))} := \frac{(2 + (0 - (7 \times (6 - 9))))}{(4 - (1 - (5 + 38)))} := \frac{(2 + (0 - (7 - 69)))}{((4 \times (1 \times (5 - 3))) \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(20 - ((7 - 6)^9))}{(4 + (1 - (5 - 38)))} := \frac{(20 - (7 - (6 + 9)))}{((4 \times (1 + (5 - 3))) - 8)} := \frac{(20 \times (7 + (6 - 9)))}{((4 + (1 + (5 \times 3))) \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(20 + (7 + 69))}{((4 - (1 - 5)) \times (3 \times 8))} := \frac{(20 + (76 + 9))}{((41 \times 5) - (3 - 8))} := \frac{(207 - (6 + 9))}{(4 \times ((15 - 3) \times 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{2076 - 9}{4 \times (1 + 5) + 38}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.60 62 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{10537}{84296} &:= \frac{(((1 - (0 - 5)) \times 3) + 7)}{(8 + ((4 - 2) \times 96))} := \frac{(((1 - (0 - 5)) \times 3) - 7)}{(8 - ((4^2) - 96))} := \frac{(((1^{05}) + 3) \times 7)}{(8 \times (4 + ((2 \times 9) + 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((1 - (0 - (5 \times 3))) \times 7)}{(8 \times (4 + (2 \times (9 \times 6))))} := \frac{(((1 - (0 - (5 + 3))) \times 7)}{(84 \times (2 \times (9 - 6)))} := \frac{(((1 - (0 - 5)) \times (3 \times 7))}{(8 \times (42 \times (9 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((1^{05}) + 37)}{(8 \times ((4 \times (2 + 9)) - 6))} := \frac{((10 \times (5 + 3)) + 7)}{((8 - 4) \times (29 \times 6))} := \frac{((10 \times (5 + 3)) - 7)}{(8 + ((4 + 2) \times 96))} \\
 &:= \frac{((10 \times (5 - 3)) - 7)}{(8 + (4 \times ((2 \times 9) + 6)))} := \frac{((10 \times 5) - (3 \times 7))}{((10 \times 5) - (3 - 7))} := \frac{((10 \times 5) - (3 - 7))}{((8 \times 42) + 96)} \\
 &:= \frac{((10^{5-3}) - 7)}{((8 + (4 \times 29)) \times 6)} := \frac{((10 + (5 - 3)) \times 7)}{(84 \times (2^9 - 6))} := \frac{((10 + 5) \times (3 \times 7))}{(84 \times (2 \times (9 + 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - ((0 \times 53) - 7))}{(8 + (4 - (2 - (9 \times 6))))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - ((5 \times 3) + 7)))}{(8 \times ((4 \times 2) + (9 + 6)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - ((5 + 3) \times 7)))}{(8 \times (42 + (9 + 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - ((5 - 3)^7))}{8 + 4^{2+9-6}} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 - (3 - 7))))}{(8 \times (4 + (2 \times (9 - 6))))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 + (3 \times 7))))}{(8 - (4 \times (2 - (9 \times 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 + (3 + 7))))}{(8 + (4 \times (2 \times (9 + 6))))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 + (3 - 7))))}{(8 - (4 - ((2 \times 9) - 6)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (53 \times 7)))}{(8 \times ((42 \times 9) - 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 \times (5 - 37)))}{8^{4^2-9-6}} := \frac{1 + 0537}{8 + 4296} := \frac{(1 \times ((0 \times 5) - (3 - 7)))}{(8 + (4 \times (2 \times (9 - 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times ((0 \times 53) + 7))}{(8 - (4 + (2 - (9 \times 6))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 - (5 - (3 + 7))))}{(8 + (4 \times (2^9 - 6)))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 - (5 \times (3 - 7))))}{(8 \times (4 \times (2 + (9 - 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 - (5 - 37)))}{(8 \times (4 \times (2^9 - 6)))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((5 \times 3) + 7)))}{(8 - (4 \times ((2 - 9) \times 6)))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((5^3) + 7)))}{(8 \times ((4 + (2 \times 9)) \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((5 + 3) \times 7))}{(8 \times (4 - (2 - (9 \times 6))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((5 + 3)^7))}{8^{(4-2)^{9-6}}} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((5 - 3) \times 7))}{(8 - (4 - (2 \times (9 \times 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((5 - 3)^7))}{((8^4) - ((2^9) \times 6))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (5 - (3 - 7))))}{(8 \times (4 + (2 + (9 - 6))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (5 \times (3 + 7))))}{(8 + (4 \times (2 + 96)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (5 + (3 + 7))))}{(8 + (4 + (2 \times (9 \times 6))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (5 + 37)))}{(8 \times (((4^2) - 9) \times 6))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (53 + 7)))}{(8 \times (4 + (2 + (9 \times 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (53 - 7)))}{(8 \times (4 - ((2 - 9) \times 6)))} := \frac{(1 + (0 - (5 - (3 \times 7))))}{(8 \times (4 - (2 - (9 + 6))))} := \frac{(1 + (0 - (5 - (3 + 7))))}{(8 \times ((4 - 2) \times (9 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (5 \times (3 - 7))))}{(8 \times (4 + (2 + (9 + 6))))} := \frac{(1 + (0 - (5 - 37)))}{((84 \times 2) + 96)} := \frac{(10 - (5 \times (3 - 7)))}{((8 \times 42) - 96)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(10 \times ((5-3) \times 7))}{(8 \times (4 \times (29+6)))} &:= \frac{(10 \times (5 - (3-7)))}{(8 \times ((4 + (2+9)) \times 6))} &:= \frac{(10 \times (5 + (3 \times 7)))}{(8 + (4 \times ((2^9) + 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 \times (5 + (3+7)))}{(8 \times (((4^2) + 9) \times 6))} &:= \frac{(10 \times (53+7))}{((8+42) \times 96)} &:= \frac{(10 + ((5 \times 3) - 7))}{(8 \times ((4+2) \times (9-6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 + ((5+3) \times 7))}{(8 \times ((4 - (2-9)) \times 6))} &:= \frac{(10 + ((5-3) \times 7))}{(8 \times (4 \times (2 \times (9-6))))} &:= \frac{(10 + ((5-3)^7))}{(8 \times (42+96))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 + (5 - (3-7)))}{(8 \times ((4^2) + (9-6)))} &:= \frac{(10 + (5 + (3 \times 7)))}{((8+4) \times ((2 \times 9) + 6))} &:= \frac{(10 + (53+7))}{(8 \times (4 + ((2+9) \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(105 - (3-7))}{(8 + ((4^2) \times (9 \times 6)))} &:= \frac{(105 - 37)}{(8 \times (4 \times (2 + (9+6))))} &
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{10638}{95742}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((1 - (0 - 6)) \times 3)^8)}{((9^5) \times (7^{4 \times 2}))} &:= \frac{(((1 - (0 - 6)) \times 3) + 8)}{(9 \times ((5 \times 7) - (4 + 2)))} &:= \frac{(((1 - (0 - 6)) \times 3) - 8)}{(9 \times ((5 \times (7 - 4)) - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((10 \times 6) - 3) \times 8)}{(9 \times (57 \times (4 \times 2)))} &:= \frac{(((10 \times 6) - 3)^8)}{(9 \times (57^{4 \times 2}))} &:= \frac{(((10 - 6) \times 3)^8)}{(9 \times ((5 + 7)^{4 \times 2}))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((10 - 6) \times 3) - 8)}{(9 \times (5 - (7 - (4 + 2))))} &:= \frac{((1 - (0 - 6)) \times (3 + 8))}{(9 \times (5 + (74 - 2)))} &:= \frac{((1^{06}) + 38)}{(9 + (57 \times (4 + 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((10 \times (6 + 3)) + 8)}{((9 + (5 + 7)) \times 42)} &:= \frac{(((10 \times 6) - (3 + 8))}{(9 \times (57 - (4 \times 2)))} &:= \frac{(((10 \times 6) + (3 \times 8))}{(9 + (5 + 742))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((10 - 6) \times (3 \times 8))}{(9 \times ((5 + 7) \times (4 \times 2)))} &:= \frac{(1 - ((0 \times 63) - 8))}{(9 + ((5 + 7) \times (4 + 2)))} &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - ((6 \times 3) + 8)))}{(9 \times (5 + ((7 + 4) \times 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - ((6^3) + 8)))}{(9 \times ((5 \times (7 - 4))^2))} &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - ((6 + 3) \times 8)))}{(9 \times (57 + (4^2)))} &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - ((6 - 3) \times 8)))}{(9 \times (5 \times (7 - (4 - 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - ((6 - 3)^8)))}{((9^5) - (7 - (4^2)))} &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (6 - (3 - 8))))}{(9 + (57 + 42))} &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (6 + (3 + 8))))}{(9 \times (5 + (7 + (4 + 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (6 + (3 - 8))))}{(9 - (5 - (7 \times (4 - 2))))} &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (6 + 38)))}{(1 - (0 - (638)))} &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (63 + 8)))}{(1 - (0 - (63 + 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 - (0 \times (6 - 38)))}{(9 - (5 - (7 - (4 - 2))))} &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - 638))}{(9 + 5742)} &:= \frac{(1 \times ((0 \times 63) + 8))}{(9 + (57 + (4 + 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 - (6 - (3 + 8))))}{(9 \times 5^{7-4-2})} &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 - (6 \times (3 - 8))))}{(9 \times (5 \times ((7 - 4) \times 2)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 - (6 - 38)))}{(9 + (57 + (4 + 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((6 \times 3) + 8)))}{(9 + ((5 \times (7 - 4))^2))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((6 \times 3) - 8)))}{(9 \times (5 + (7 - (4 - 2))))} &:= \frac{(9 \times ((5 + (7 + 4)) \times 2))}{(9 \times ((5 + 7) \times (4 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((6 - 3)^8)))}{g^{57-4-2}} &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (6 - (3 - 8))))}{(9 \times (5 + ((7 - 4) \times 2)))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (6 \times (3 \times 8))))}{(9 \times ((5 + 7)^{4-2}))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (6 \times (3^8))))}{((9^5) \times ((7 - 4) \times 2))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (6 \times (3 + 8))))}{(9 \times ((5 + (7 \times 4)) \times 2))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (6 + (3 + 8))))}{(9 \times ((5 \times (7 - 4)) + 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (6 + 38)))}{((9 + 57) \times (4 + 2))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (63 \times 8)))}{(9 \times ((5 + 7) \times 42))} &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (63 - 8)))}{(9 \times (57 - (4 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + 638))}{(957 \times (4 + 2))} &:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (6 - (3 \times 8))))}{(9 \times (5 + (7 \times (4 - 2))))} &:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (6 - (3 + 8))))}{(9 - (5 \times (7 - (4^2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (6 \times (3 - 8))))}{(9 \times (5 + ((7 \times 4) - 2)))} &:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (6 - 38)))}{(9 \times ((5 \times 7) - (4 - 2)))} &:= \frac{(9 - (5 \times (7 - (4^2))))}{(10 - (6 - (3 \times 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 - (6 - (3 + 8)))}{(9 + (5 + ((7 + 4)^2)))} &:= \frac{(10 - (6 \times (3 - 8)))}{(9 \times (5 - (7 - 42)))} &:= \frac{(10 - (6 - (3 \times 8)))}{(9 \times (5 + (7 + (4^2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 \times (6 + (3 + 8)))}{(9 + (((5 \times 7) + 4)^2))} &:= \frac{(10 + ((6 \times 3) + 8))}{((9 \times (5 - (7 - 4)))^2)} &:= \frac{(10 + ((6 \times 3) - 8))}{(9 \times (5 + (7 + (4 \times 2))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(10 + (6 + 38))}{(9 \times (5 + (7 + 42)))} & := \frac{(10 + (63 + 8))}{(9 \times (5 + (74 + 2)))} & := \frac{(10 + (63 - 8))}{(9 \times (5 \times (7 + (4 + 2))))} \\
 & := \frac{(106 - (3 + 8))}{(95 \times (7 + (4 - 2)))} & := \frac{(106 - (3 - 8))}{(957 + 42)} & := \frac{(106 + (3 \times 8))}{(9 \times (5 \times ((7 \times 4) - 2)))} \\
 & := \frac{(106 + (3 + 8))}{(9 \times (5 + (7 \times (4^2))))} & := \frac{(106 - 38)}{((95 + 7) \times (4 + 2))} & \\
 \rightarrow \frac{48516}{97032} & := \frac{(((4 \times (8 \times 5)) - 1) \times 6)}{(9 \times ((70 \times 3) + 2))} & := \frac{(((4 \times (8 - 5)) - 1) \times 6)}{((9 \times (7 - 0)) + 3) \times 2} & := \frac{(((4 \times 8) - 5) \times (1 + 6))}{(9 \times (7 \times (0 + (3 \times 2))))} \\
 & := \frac{(((4 \times (8 + (5 \times 1))) - 6)}{((9 \times (7 - (0 - 3))) + 2)} & := \frac{(((4 \times (8 + (5 - 1))) + 6)}{(9 \times (7 - (0 - (3 + 2))))} & := \frac{(((4 \times (8 + 5)) - (1^6))}{(97 - (0 - (3 + 2)))} \\
 & := \frac{(((4 \times (8 - 5)) - (1 + 6))}{(9 + (7 + (0 - (3 \times 2))))} & := \frac{(((4 \times (85 - 1)) + 6)}{(9 \times (70 + (3 \times 2)))} & := \frac{(((4 \times 8) - (5 - (1 + 6))))}{((9 \times (7 - 0)) + (3 + 2))} \\
 & := \frac{((4^{8-5}) - (1^6))}{(9 \times (7 \times ((0 \times 3) + 2)))} & := \frac{(((4 + (8 - 5)) \times (1 + 6))}{(97 - (0 - (3 - 2)))} & := \frac{(4 - ((8 - 5) \times (1 - 6)))}{((9 + (7 - (0 - 3))) \times 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(4 - (8 - (5 \times (1 + 6))))}{((9 \times (7 - 0)) - (3 - 2))} & := \frac{(4 - (8 - (5 + (1^6))))}{(9 - (7 + ((0 \times 3) - 2)))} & := \frac{(4 - (8 - (5 + 16)))}{(9 - (7 + (0 - 32)))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 - (8 - (51 + 6)))}{(97 - (0 - (3^2)))} & := \frac{(4 - (8 \times (5 + (1 - 6))))}{(9 - (7 + (0 - (3 \times 2))))} & := \frac{(4 - (8 + (5 - 16)))}{(9 + (7 + ((0 \times 3) - 2)))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times (((8 \times 5) - 1) \times 6))}{(9 \times ((70 \times 3) - 2))} & := \frac{(4 \times ((8 + (5 \times 1)) \times 6))}{((9 \times 70) - (3 \times 2))} & := \frac{(4 \times ((8 + (5 - 1)) \times 6))}{(9 \times (70 - (3 \times 2)))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times (8 - (5 - (1^6))))}{(9 - ((7 \times (0 - 3)) - 2))} & := \frac{(4 \times (8 - (5 - (1 + 6))))}{(9 + (70 + (3 - 2)))} & := \frac{(4 \times (8 - (5 + (1 - 6))))}{((9 - (7 - 0)) \times 32)} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times (8 - (5 - 16)))}{((9 + (70 - 3)) \times 2)} & := \frac{(4 \times (8 \times ((5 + 1) \times 6)))}{(((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 3)^2)} & := \frac{(4 \times (8 \times (5 - (1^6))))}{((9 + (7 - (0 \times 3)))^2)} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times (8 + (5 - (1^6))))}{((9 + (7 - 0)) \times (3 \times 2))} & := \frac{(4 \times (8 + (5 - (1 + 6))))}{(9 + (7 - (0 - 32)))} & := \frac{(4 \times (8 + (5 - (1 - 6))))}{(9 \times (7 - (0 - (3^2))))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times (8 + (5 \times 16)))}{((9 + (7^03)) \times 2)} & := \frac{4^{8-5+16}}{((9 - (7 - 0))^{3^2})} & := \frac{4^{8+5-1-6}}{(((9 + (7 - 0))^3) \times 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + ((8 \times (5 - 1)) - 6))}{((9 - (7 \times (0 - 3))) \times 2)} & := \frac{(4 + ((8 \times 5) + (1 - 6)))}{(9 + (70 - (3 - 2)))} & := \frac{(4 + ((8 \times 5) + 16))}{(((9 \times (7 - 0)) - 3) \times 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + ((8 + (5 \times 1)) \times 6))}{((9 + (70 + 3)) \times 2)} & := \frac{(4 + ((8 - 5) \times (1 + 6)))}{((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 3) + 2} & := \frac{(4 + (8 - (5 - (1 \times 6))))}{((9 + (7 + (0 - 3))) \times 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + (8 - (5 - (1^6))))}{(9 + (7 - (0 \times 32)))} & := \frac{(4 + (8 - (5 - (1 + 6))))}{(9 - ((7 \times (0 - 3)) + 2))} & := \frac{(4 + (8 - (5 \times (1 - 6))))}{(9 + (70 - (3 + 2)))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + (8 - (5 + (1^6))))}{((9 - (7 - 0)) \times (3 \times 2))} & := \frac{(4 + (8 - (5 - 16)))}{(((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 3) - 2)} & := \frac{(4 + (8 \times (5 - (1^6))))}{(9 - (7 \times (0 - (3^2))))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + (8 \times (5 \times (1^6))))}{((9 \times (7 - (0 - 3))) - 2)} & := \frac{(4 + (8 \times (5 + (1 + 6))))}{((97 - (0 - 3)) \times 2)} & := \frac{(4 + (8 + (5 - (1 \times 6))))}{(9 + (7 - (0 - (3 \times 2))))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + (8 + (5 - (1 - 6))))}{(9 - (7 \times (0 - (3 + 2))))} & := \frac{(4 + (8 + (5 \times (1 \times 6))))}{(9 + (70 + (3 + 2)))} & := \frac{(4 + (8 + (5 + (1^6))))}{(((9 - (7 - 0)) \times 3)^2)} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + (8 + (51 \times 6)))}{((9 \times 70) + (3 \times 2))} & := \frac{(4 + (8 + (5 - 16)))}{(9 - (7 - (0 \times 32)))} & := \frac{(4 + (85 - (1 - 6)))}{((97 + (0 - 3)) \times 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + (85 + (1^6)))}{(9 \times ((7 - (0 - 3)) \times 2))} & := \frac{(48 - (5 + 16))}{(9 \times (7 + (0 - (3 - 2))))} & := \frac{(48 - (51 - 6))}{(((9 - (7 - 0))^3) - 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(48 \times (5 + 16))}{(9 \times (7 \times (0 + 32)))} & := \frac{(485 \times (1 \times 6))}{(970 \times (3 \times 2))} & := \frac{(485 \times (1^6))}{(970 \times (3 - 2))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(485 + 16)}{(970 + 32)} \quad := \frac{(485 - 16)}{(970 - 32)}$$

3.61 63 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{45138}{90276} &:= \frac{(((4 \times 5) - 1) \times 3) + 8}{(90 - (2 - (7 \times 6)))} := \frac{(((4 \times 5) + 1) \times (3 + 8))}{((9 - (0 - 2)) \times (7 \times 6))} := \frac{(((4 + (5 \times 1)) \times 3) + 8)}{(90 - ((2 \times 7) + 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times (5 \times 1)) + 38)}{(90 + (2 \times (7 + 6)))} := \frac{(((4 \times (5 \times (1^3))) - 8)}{(9 - (0 - (2 + (7 + 6))))} := \frac{4^{5-1^3} \times 8}{((9 - (0 - (2 - 7)))^6)} \\
 &:= \frac{4^{5-1^3} + 8}{(((9^0)^2) + 7) \times 6} := \frac{4^{5+1^3} - 8}{((9^0)^2) + 76} := \frac{((4 + (5 \times 1)) \times 38)}{(9 \times ((0 \times 2) + 76))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 + (5 \times (1^3))) \times 8)}{(90 + ((2 + 7) \times 6))} := \frac{((4 + 5) \times (1 + 38))}{(9 \times (0 + (2 + 76)))} := \frac{((4 + 5) \times 138)}{(9 \times (0 + 276))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (5 - (1 - (3 - 8))))}{(9 - (0 - (2 - (7 - 6))))} := \frac{(4 - (5 - (1 \times (3 \times 8))))}{(90 - (2 + (7 \times 6)))} := \frac{(4 - (5 - (1 \times (3 + 8))))}{(9 + (0 - (2 - (7 + 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (5 - (1 + (3 + 8))))}{(9 - ((0 \times 2) - (7 + 6)))} := \frac{(4 - (5 - (1 + 38)))}{((9 \times (0 \times 2)) + 76)} := \frac{(4 - (5 \times (1 - (3 + 8))))}{((9 - (0 - (2 + 7))) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (5 \times (1 \times (3 - 8))))}{((9 \times (0 - 2)) + 76)} := \frac{(4 - (5 \times (1 - 38)))}{(9 \times ((0 \times 2) + (7 \times 6)))} := \frac{(4 - (5 + ((1^3) - 8))}{(9 - (0 - (2 + (7 - 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (5 + (1 - (3 + 8))))}{(9 \times (0 + (2 \times (7 - 6))))} := \frac{(4 - (5 + (1 - 38)))}{(9 \times (0 + ((2 \times 7) - 6)))} := \frac{(4 \times ((5 - (1^3)) \times 8))}{((90 \times 2) + 76)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times ((5 \times 13) - 8))}{((90 - (2 \times 7)) \times 6)} := \frac{(4 \times (5 - ((1 - 3) \times 8)))}{(90 + (2 + 76))} := \frac{(4 \times (5 - (1 - (3 \times 8))))}{(90 + ((2^7) + 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (5 - (1 - (3 + 8))))}{((9 \times (0 + (2 \times 7))) - 6)} := \frac{(4 \times (5 - (1 \times (3 - 8))))}{((9^0)^2) - (7 - 6)} := \frac{(4 \times (5 \times ((1^3) + 8)))}{(9 \times (0 - (2 - (7 \times 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (5 + ((1^3) \times 8)))}{((90 \times 2) - 76)} := \frac{(4 \times (5 + (1 - (3 - 8))))}{(90 - (2 \times (7 - 6)))} := \frac{(4 \times (5 + 138))}{((90 - 2) \times (7 + 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (51 - (3 \times 8)))}{((9 - (0 - 27)) \times 6)} := \frac{(4^{5+1+3-8})}{(9 + (0 - (2 - (7 - 6))))} := \frac{(4 + ((5 \times (1 \times 3)) + 8))}{(9 \times ((0 \times 27) + 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + ((5 \times (1 \times 3)) - 8))}{(90 + (2 \times 76))} := \frac{(4 + (5 - ((1^3)^8)))}{(90 + (2 - 76))} := \frac{(4 + (5 - ((1 - 3) \times 8)))}{(90 + (2 - (7 \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (5 - (1 - (3 \times 8))))}{((9 + ((0 \times 2) - 7))^6)} := \frac{(4 + (5 - (1 - (3 - 8))))}{(9 + (0 - (2 + (7 - 6))))} := \frac{(4 + (5 - (1 - 38)))}{(90 + (2 \times (7 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (5 \times ((1^3) + 8)))}{(90 + ((2 \times 7) - 6))} := \frac{(4 + (5 \times (1 - (3 - 8))))}{((9^0)^2) - (7 + 6)} := \frac{(4 + (5 + ((1^3) + 8)))}{(90 - ((2 + 7) \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (5 + ((1 + 3) \times 8)))}{((9^0)^2) + (7 - 6)} := \frac{(4 + (5 + (1 - (3 - 8))))}{(9 - (0 - (27 - 6)))} := \frac{(4 + (5 + (1 \times (3 \times 8))))}{(((9 \times (0 + 2)) - 7) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (5 + (1 \times 38)))}{((9^0)^2) + (7 + 6)} := \frac{(4 + (5 + (1 + (3 + 8))))}{(9 - (0 - (27 + 6)))} := \frac{(4 + (5 + (1 + 38)))}{((9 - ((0 \times 2) - 7)) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (5 + (13 + 8)))}{((9 \times (0 + 2)) + (7 \times 6))} := \frac{(4 + (5 + 138))}{((9 + (0 - 2)) \times (7 \times 6))} := \frac{(4 + (51 + (3 + 8)))}{((9 \times (0 + (2 \times 7))) + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(45 - (1 - (3 + 8)))}{(90 + ((2 \times 7) + 6))} := \frac{(45 - (1 - 38))}{(90 - (2 - 76))} := \frac{(45 \times ((1^3) \times 8))}{(90 \times ((2 \times 7) - 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(45 \times (13 + 8))}{(90 \times (27 - 6))} := \frac{45 \times 1^{38}}{90^{2-7+6}} := \frac{(45 + (1 \times (3 \times 8)))}{((9 - (0 - (2 \times 7))) \times 6)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{45 + 138}{90 + 276} \qquad := \frac{451 + 38}{902 + 76} \qquad := \frac{451 - 38}{902 - 76}$$

3.62 64 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned} \blacktriangleright \frac{10953}{87624} &:= \frac{(((1+09) \times 5) + 3)}{(((8 \times (7+6)) + 2) \times 4)} := \frac{(((1+09) \times 5) - 3)}{(8 \times (7 + ((6^2) + 4)))} := \frac{(((10 \times 9) - 5) \times 3)}{(8 \times (7 + (62 \times 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{((1 - (0 - (9 - 5))) \times 3)}{(8 \times (7 + (6 - (2 - 4))))} := \frac{((1+09) \times (5 \times 3))}{((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 24)} := \frac{((1+09) \times (5^3))}{((8 + ((7 - 6) \times 2))^4)} \\ &:= \frac{((1+09) \times (5 + 3))}{(8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times 2)) - 4))} := \frac{((1+09) \times (5 - 3))}{(8 - (76 \times (2 - 4)))} := \frac{((1+09)^{5-3})}{(8 \times (76 + 24))} \\ &:= \frac{((1^{09}) + (5 \times 3))}{(8 \times ((7 - 6) \times (2^4)))} := \frac{((1^{09}) + (5 + 3))}{(8 \times (7 - (6 - (2 \times 4))))} := \frac{((10 \times (9 - 5)) - 3)}{(8 \times (7 + (6 + 24)))} \\ &:= \frac{((10 \times 9) - (5 \times 3))}{((8 \times 76) - (2 \times 4))} := \frac{((10 \times 9) - (5 - 3))}{(8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times 2)) + 4))} := \frac{((10 + (9 \times 5)) \times 3)}{(8 \times (((7 + 6)^2) - 4))} \\ &:= \frac{((10 + 9) \times (5 - 3))}{(8 + ((76 - 2) \times 4))} := \frac{((109 - 5) \times 3)}{(8 \times ((76 + 2) \times 4))} := \frac{(1 - ((0 \times 95) - 3))}{(8 + ((7 \times (6 - 2)) - 4))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - ((9 + 5) \times 3)))}{(8 \times (7 + (6 \times (2 + 4))))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - ((9 - 5) \times 3)))}{(((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 2) + 4)} := \frac{(1 - (0 - ((9 - 5)^3)))}{(8 \times (7 + (62 - 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 - (5 + 3))))}{(8 + ((7 - 6) \times (2 \times 4)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 - (5 - 3))))}{(1 - (0 - (9 - (5 - 3))))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 \times (5 + 3))))}{(8 \times (7 + (62 + 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 \times (5 - 3))))}{(8 \times (7 - (6 \times (2 - 4))))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (9^{5-3})))}{(8 \times (76 + (2 + 4)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 + (5 \times 3))))}{(8 \times (7 - (6 - 24)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 + (5 - 3))))}{(8 \times ((7 - (6 - 2)) \times 4))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (9 + 53)))}{((8 + 76) \times (2 + 4))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (95 - 3)))}{((87 + 6) \times (2 \times 4))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (0 \times (9 - 53)))}{(8 - (7 \times (6 - (2 + 4))))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - 953))}{(8 + 7624)} := \frac{(1 \times ((0 \times 95) + 3))}{(8 \times (7 - (6 + (2 - 4))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 - (9 - (5 \times 3))))}{(8 \times ((7 - 6) \times (2 + 4)))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 - (9 - 53)))}{(8 \times ((7 + (6 - 2)) \times 4))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((9 \times 5) + 3)))}{(8 \times ((7 \times 6) + (2 + 4)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((9 + 5) \times 3)))}{((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (2^4))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((9 - 5)^3)))}{8^{7-6-2+4}} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 - (5 - 3))))}{(8 \times (7 - (6 - (2 + 4))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 \times (5 - 3))))}{((8 + (7 \times (6 - 2))) \times 4)} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9^{5-3})))}{(8 \times ((7 - (6 - 2))^4))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 + (5 \times 3))))}{(8 \times ((7 \times (6 - 2)) - 4))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 + (5 + 3))))}{(8 \times (7 - (6 - (2^4))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 + (5 - 3))))}{(8 \times (7 + (6 + (2 - 4))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (9 + 53)))}{(((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (2 \times 4))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (95 + 3)))}{(8 \times (7 \times (6 + (2 \times 4))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (95 - 3)))}{(8 \times (76 + (2^4)))} := \frac{(1 + (0 - (9 - 53)))}{((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 24)} \\ &:= \frac{(10 \times ((9 \times 5) + 3))}{((8 + 7) \times ((6 - 2)^4))} := \frac{(10 \times (9 - (5 - 3)))}{(8 \times (76 - (2 + 4)))} := \frac{(10 \times (9 \times (5 - 3)))}{((8 + 7) \times (6 \times (2^4)))} \\ &:= \frac{10^{9-5-3}}{((8 \times (7 + 6)) - 24)} := \frac{(10 + ((9 \times 5) + 3))}{(8 + (76 \times (2 + 4)))} := \frac{(10 + ((9 + 5) \times 3))}{(8 \times ((7 \times (6 + 2)) - 4))} \\ &:= \frac{(10 + ((9 - 5) \times 3))}{(8 \times (((7 + 6) \times 2) - 4))} := \frac{(10 + ((9 - 5)^3))}{(8 \times (76 + (2 - 4)))} := \frac{(10 + (9 \times (5 - 3)))}{(8 \times (7 \times (6 + (2 - 4))))} \\ &:= \frac{(10 + (9 + (5 \times 3)))}{(8 \times ((7 \times 6) - (2 \times 4)))} := \frac{(10 + (9 + (5 + 3)))}{((8 + (7 - 6)) \times 24)} := \frac{(10 + (9 + (5 - 3)))}{(8 \times (7 + (6 + (2 \times 4))))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(109 \times (5 - 3))}{(8 + (7 \times (62 \times 4)))} &:= \frac{(109 + (5 \times 3))}{(((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (2^4))} &:= \frac{(109 + 53)}{((8 - ((7 - 6) \times 2))^4)} \\ &:= \frac{(109 - 53)}{(8 \times (7 \times (6 - (2 - 4))))} \end{aligned}$$

► **27309**
54618

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(((2 \times 7) + (3 - 0)) \times 9)}{((54 \times 6) - 18)} &:= \frac{(((2 + 7) \times 30) - 9)}{((5 + (4 \times 6)) \times 18)} &:= \frac{((2 - (7 \times 3)) \times (0 - 9))}{((54 \times 6) + 18)} \\ &:= \frac{((2 - (7 - 3)) \times (0 - 9))}{(5 + ((4 \times 6) - (1 - 8)))} &:= \frac{((2 - (7 - 30)) \times 9)}{(5 \times ((4 + 6) \times (1 + 8)))} &:= \frac{((2 \times (7 - (3 - 0))) + 9)}{((5 \times 4) + (6 + (1 \times 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{((2 \times (7 \times (3 - 0))) + 9)}{((5 \times (4 \times 6)) - 18)} &:= \frac{((2 \times (7 \times (3 - 0))) - 9)}{(54 - (6 - 18))} &:= \frac{((2 \times (7 + (3 - 0))) + 9)}{((5 \times (4 + (6 \times 1))) + 8)} \\ &:= \frac{((2 \times (7 + (3 - 0))) - 9)}{(5 + (4 + (6 - (1 - 8))))} &:= \frac{(2 \times 7)^{3+0 \times 9}}{(((5^4) + 61) \times 8)} &:= \frac{((2 \times 7) + (30 - 9))}{(5 - (4 - (61 + 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{((2^{7-3+0}) + 9)}{(5 \times (4 + (6 \times (1^8))))} &:= \frac{((2^7) - (3 - (0 - 9)))}{((5 + (4 \times (6 \times 1))) \times 8)} &:= \frac{((2^7) + (3 - (0 \times 9)))}{((54 \times (6 - 1)) - 8)} \\ &:= \frac{((2^7) + (3 - (0 - 9)))}{(5 \times (4 \times (6 + (1 \times 8))))} &:= \frac{((2 + (7 - (3 - 0))) \times 9)}{((5 \times (4 \times (6 - 1))) + 8)} &:= \frac{((2 + (7 + (3 - 0))) \times 9)}{((5 + 4) \times (6 + 18))} \\ &:= \frac{((2 + (7 + 30)) \times 9)}{(54 \times (6 - (1 - 8)))} &:= \frac{((2 + 7) \times (3 \times (0 + 9)))}{((2 + 7) \times (3 \times (0 + 9)))} &:= \frac{((2 + 7) \times (30 - 9))}{(54 \times (6 + (1^8)))} \\ &:= \frac{((2 + 7) \times 309)}{((5 + 4) \times 618)} &:= \frac{((27 - (3 - 0)) \times 9)}{((54 - 6) \times (1 + 8))} &:= \frac{(5 \times (46 + (1 \times 8)))}{((2 - 7) \times (3 \times (0 - 9)))} \\ &:= \frac{((27 \times (3 - 0)) + 9)}{(5 \times ((4 \times (6 + 1)) + 8))} &:= \frac{((54 + 6) \times (1 + 8))}{((54 + 6) \times (1 + 8))} &:= \frac{(5 + (4 + (6 - (1^8))))}{(2 - (7 - (30 + 9)))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (7 - (30 + 9)))}{((5 \times (4 + 6)) + 18)} &:= \frac{(2 - (7 + (3 \times (0 - 9))))}{(5 + (46 + (1 - 8)))} &:= \frac{(2 - (7 + (3 + (0 - 9))))}{(5 + (4 - (6 + (1^8))))} \\ &:= \frac{((5 \times (4 + 6)) + 18)}{(2 \times ((7 \times (3 - 0)) + 9))} &:= \frac{(2 \times ((7 \times (3 - 0)) - 9))}{(2 \times ((7 \times (3 - 0)) - 9))} &:= \frac{(2 \times ((7 + (3 - 0)) \times 9))}{(2 \times ((7 + (3 - 0)) \times 9))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 \times (4 \times (6 \times (1^8))))}{(2 \times (7 - (3 - (0 \times 9))))} &:= \frac{((5 - (4 - (6 - 1))) \times 8)}{(2 \times (7 - (3 \times (0 \times 9))))} &:= \frac{(5 \times ((4 + (6 - 1)) \times 8))}{(2 \times (7 - (3 + (0 - 9))))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + (4 + (6 + (1^8))))}{(2 \times (7 \times (3 \times (0 + 9))))} &:= \frac{(5 + ((4 \times 6) - (1^8)))}{(2 \times (7 + (3 - (0 \times 9))))} &:= \frac{(5 + (46 + (1^8)))}{(2 \times (7 + (3 - (0 - 9))))} \\ &:= \frac{(54 \times (6 + (1 \times 8)))}{(2 \times (7 + (30 - 9)))} &:= \frac{(54 - (6 + (1 \times 8)))}{2^{7-3+0 \times 9}} &:= \frac{((5 \times 4) + ((6 + 1) \times 8))}{2^7 + 3 \times 0 \times 9} \\ &:= \frac{((5 \times (4 \times (6 \times 1))) - 8)}{2^{7+3-09}} &:= \frac{((5 + (4 - (6 - 1))) \times 8)}{(2 + ((7 \times (3 - 0)) + 9))} &:= \frac{((5 + (4 - (6 + 1)))^8)}{(2 + ((7^3 + 0) - 9))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + (4 - (6 - (1^8))))}{(2 + (7 - (3 - (0 \times 9))))} &:= \frac{((5 - (4 - (6 + 1))) \times 8)}{(2 + (7 - (3 \times (0 \times 9))))} &:= \frac{(54 + 618)}{(2 + (7 - (3 \times (0 - 9))))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 + (4 - (6 - (1 + 8))))}{(2 + (7 - (3 + (0 - 9))))} &:= \frac{(((5 - 4)^6) \times 18)}{(2 + (7 \times (3 - (0 \times 9))))} &:= \frac{(((5 + 4) \times 6) + 18)}{(2 + (7 + (3 - (0 \times 9))))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 \times (4 - (6 - (1 \times 8))))}{(2 + (7 + (3 - (0 - 9))))} &:= \frac{(((5 + 4) \times (6 \times 1)) - 8)}{(2 + (7 + (3 + (0 - 9))))} &:= \frac{(5 + (4 + (6 + (1 + 8))))}{(2 + (7 + (30 + 9)))} \\ &:= \frac{((5 \times (4 + (6 \times 1))) - 8)}{(2 + (7 + (30 - 9)))} &:= \frac{(5 - (4 - (6 - (1^8))))}{(2 + (73 + (0 - 9)))} &:= \frac{(54 - (6 \times (1 - 8)))}{(27 - (3 \times (0 \times 9)))} \\ &:= \frac{(5 \times ((4 \times (6 - 1)) - 8))}{(27 \times (3 - (0 \times 9)))} &:= \frac{((5 \times (4 \times (6 + 1))) - 8)}{(27 \times (3 - (0 - 9)))} &:= \frac{(5 - (4 - (61 - 8)))}{(27 + (3 - (0 - 9)))} \\ &:= \frac{(54 + (6 \times 18))}{(273 - (0 \times 9))} &:= \frac{(((5 \times 4) + 61) \times 8)}{(273 - (0 - 9))} &:= \frac{(5 + (4 + (61 + 8)))}{(273 \times (0 + 9))} \\ &:= \frac{(546 \times (1^8))}{(546 \times (1 + 8))} &:= \frac{(546 + 18)}{(546 + 18)} &:= \frac{(546 \times (1 + 8))}{(546 \times (1 + 8))} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= \frac{(273 + (0 - 9))}{(546 - 18)}$$

► **32907**
65814

$$:= \frac{(((3^2) \times (9 - 0)) - 7)}{(((6 \times 5) + (8 - 1)) \times 4)} := \frac{(((3^2) + (9 - 0)) \times 7)}{((6 + (58 - 1)) \times 4)} := \frac{(((3 + 2) \times (9 - 0)) - 7)}{((6 + (5 + (8 \times 1))) \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{(((3 - 2)^9 + 0) + 7)}{(6 + (5 + (8 + (1 - 4))))} := \frac{((3 - (2 \times 9)) \times (0 - 7))}{(6 \times (5 \times (8 - (1^4))))} := \frac{((3 - (2 + 9)) \times (0 - 7))}{((6 - 5) \times (8 \times 14))}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 \times (2 + (9 - 0))) + 7)}{((6 + (5 + (8 + 1))) \times 4)} := \frac{((3 \times (2 + (9 - 0))) - 7)}{(65 - (8 + (1 + 4)))} := \frac{((3 \times (2 + 90)) + 7)}{(6 + (5 \times (8 \times 14)))}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 \times (29 - 0)) + 7)}{(6 + ((5 + 8) \times 14))} := \frac{((3 \times 2) - (9 + (0 - 7)))}{(6 - (5 - (8 - (1^4))))} := \frac{((3 \times 2)^{9-07})}{(6 \times (5 + (8 - (1^4))))}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 \times 2) + (9 - (0 - 7)))}{((6 + 5) \times (8 - (1 \times 4)))} := \frac{((3 \times 2) + (90 + 7))}{(6 + (5 \times (8 \times (1 + 4))))} := \frac{((3^2) \times (9 - (0 - 7)))}{(6 \times ((5 + (8 - 1)) \times 4))}$$

$$:= \frac{((3^2) \times (9 + (0 - 7)))}{(6 - (5 \times (8 - 14)))} := \frac{((3^2) + (9 + (0 - 7)))}{(6 + (5 + (8 - (1 - 4))))} := \frac{((3^2) + (90 - 7))}{((6 + (5 \times (8 \times 1))) \times 4)}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 + (2 \times (9 - 0))) \times 7)}{(6 \times ((5 \times (8 + 1)) + 4))} := \frac{((3 + 2) \times (9 - (0 \times 7)))}{(6 \times (5 \times (8 - (1 + 4))))} := \frac{((3 - 2) \times (9 \times (0 + 7)))}{(6 - (5 \times (8 \times (1 - 4))))}$$

$$:= \frac{((3 - 2) \times (9 + (0 - 7)))}{(6 + (5 - (8 - (1^4))))} := \frac{((3 - 2) \times (9 + (0 - 7)))}{(6 + (5 - (8 - (1^4))))} := \frac{((3 - 2) \times (90 - 7))}{(6 + (5 \times (8 \times (1 \times 4))))}$$

$$:= \frac{(3 - (2 - (9 - (0 \times 7))))}{(6 + (5 + (8 + (1^4))))} := \frac{(3 - (2 - (9 - (0 - 7))))}{((6 \times 5) + (8 - (1 \times 4)))} := \frac{(6 + (5 - (8 + (1^4))))}{(3 - (2 - (9 \times (0 \times 7))))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 - (5 - (8 + (1 - 4))))}{(3 \times (2 - (9 \times (0 \times 7))))} := \frac{(6 \times ((5 \times 8) - (1 - 4)))}{(3 \times (2 - (9 \times (0 - 7))))} := \frac{(3 \times ((2 \times (9 - 0)) + 7))}{(3 \times ((2 \times (9 - 0)) + 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 - (5 - (8 - (1 - 4))))}{(3 \times (2 - (9 \times (0 \times 7))))} := \frac{(6 \times (5 \times (8 + (1 + 4))))}{(3 \times (2 - (9 \times (0 - 7))))} := \frac{(6 \times (5 \times (8 + (1 - 4))))}{(3 \times (2^{9-07}))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 - (5 - (8 - (1 - 4))))}{(3 \times (2 + (9 - (0 \times 7))))} := \frac{(6 \times (5 \times (8 + (1 + 4))))}{(3 \times (2 + (9 - (0 - 7))))} := \frac{(6 + (5 + (8 + (1 + 4))))}{(3 \times (29 - (0 \times 7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times (5 - (8 - 14)))}{(3 \times (29 - (0 - 7)))} := \frac{(6 \times (5 + (8 + (1 + 4))))}{(3 \times (29 + (0 - 7)))} := \frac{(6 \times (5 - (8 \times (1 - 4))))}{(3^2 + 9 \times 0 \times 7)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times ((5 \times (8 \times 1)) - 4))}{3^{2^{9-07}}} := \frac{((6 + 5) \times (8 + (1 \times 4)))}{(3 + ((2 \times (9 - 0)) + 7))} := \frac{(6 + (5 + (8 - (1^4))))}{(3 + ((2 \times 90) - 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 \times (5 + (8 + 14)))}{(3 + (2 - (9 \times (0 \times 7))))} := \frac{(65 - (8 + (1^4)))}{(3 + (2 \times (9 - (0 - 7))))} := \frac{((6 \times (58 \times 1)) + 4)}{(3 + (2 \times (90 - 7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 - (5 - (8 + (1^4))))}{3 + 2^{9-07}} := \frac{(65 + (8 + (1 - 4)))}{(3 + (2 + (9 - (0 \times 7))))} := \frac{((6 \times (58 - 1)) - 4)}{(3 + (2 + (9 - (0 - 7))))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 + (5 + (8 - (1 + 4))))}{(3 + (2 + (90 + 7)))} := \frac{((6 - 5) \times ((8 - 1) \times 4))}{(3 + (29 - (0 \times 7)))} := \frac{(6 + ((5 \times (8 \times 1)) - 4))}{(3 + (29 - (0 - 7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{((6 + (5 \times (8 + 1))) \times 4)}{(3 + (29 + (0 - 7)))} := \frac{(6 + (58 \times (1^4)))}{(3 + 2907)} := \frac{(6 \times (5 + (8 \times (1^4))))}{(32 - (9 - (0 \times 7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 + ((5 \times (8 \times 1)) + 4))}{(32 - (9 - (0 - 7)))} := \frac{(6 + 5814)}{(32 - (9 \times (0 - 7)))} := \frac{(6 + (5 \times (8 \times (1^4))))}{(32 - (9 + (0 - 7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{((6 - (5 - (8 - 1))) \times 4)}{(32 + (9 - (0 \times 7)))} := \frac{(((6 \times 5) + 8) \times (1 + 4))}{(32 + (9 - (0 - 7)))} := \frac{(6 \times (5 + (8 + (1 - 4))))}{(32 + (9 + (0 - 7)))}$$

$$:= \frac{((6 \times (5 + (8 \times 1))) + 4)}{(32 + (90 - 7))} := \frac{(6 \times (5 + (8 - (1 - 4))))}{(329 - (0 \times 7))} := \frac{((6 \times (5 + (8 - 1))) - 4)}{(329 - (0 - 7))}$$

$$:= \frac{((6 \times ((5 \times 8) - 1)) - 4)}{(329 + (0 - 7))} := \frac{(658 \times (1^4))}{(658 + 14)}$$

$$:= \frac{(6 + (5 \times 8)) \times 14}{(6 + (5 \times 8)) \times 14}$$

3.63 67 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{48615}{97230} &:= \frac{(((4 \times 8) - (6 - 1)) \times 5)}{(9 \times (7 + (23 - 0)))} := \frac{(((4 \times 8) - (6 - 1))^5)}{((9^7) \times (2 \times (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(((4 + 8) \times 6) + 15)}{((9 + (7^2)) \times (3 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 - (8 - (6 + 1))) \times 5)}{(9 - (7 + (2 - 30)))} := \frac{((4 \times (8 \times (6 + 1))) - 5)}{((9 \times (7^2)) - (3 - 0))} := \frac{((4 \times (8 \times 6)) + (1 + 5))}{(9 \times ((7 \times 2) + 30))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times (8 \times 6)) + 15)}{(9 \times ((7^2) - (3 - 0)))} := \frac{((4 \times (8 + (6 \times 1))) - 5)}{((97 + (2 + (3 - 0))))} := \frac{((4 \times (86 \times 1)) - 5)}{((9 \times 72) + 30)} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times (86 - 1)) + 5)}{((9 + (7 \times 2)) \times 30)} := \frac{((4 + (8 + (6 - 1))) \times 5)}{(9 + (7 \times (23 - 0)))} := \frac{((4 + (8 + 6)) \times 15)}{((9 + (7 + 2)) \times 30)} \\
 &:= \frac{((48 - (6 \times 1)) \times 5)}{(9 + (7 - 2)) \times 30} := \frac{((48 + (6 \times 1))^5)}{(972^3 + 0)} := \frac{(4 - (8 - ((6 + 1) \times 5)))}{(9 - (7 - (2 \times 30)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (8 - (6 - (1^5))))}{(9 + (7 \times (2 - (3 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 - (8 - (6 + 15)))}{(9 - (7 - (2 + 30)))} := \frac{(4 - (8 + (6 - 15)))}{(9 - (7 - (2^3 + 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times ((8 - (6 - 1))^5))}{(9 \times (72 \times (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times ((8 \times 6) + 15))}{(9 \times (7 \times (2^3 + 0)))} := \frac{(4 \times (8 - (6 - (1^5))))}{(9 + (7 + (2^3 + 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (8 - (6 - (1 + 5))))}{((9 - (7 - 2))^3 + 0)} := \frac{(4 \times (8 - (6 \times (1 - 5))))}{((9 - 7)^{2^3+0})} := \frac{(4 \times (8 - (6 \times (1^5))))}{(9 - (7 \times (2 - (3 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (8 - (6 + (1 - 5))))}{(9 + (7 + (2 + 30)))} := \frac{(4 \times (8 \times (6 + (1 + 5))))}{(((9 + 7)^2) \times (3 - 0))} := \frac{4 \times 8^{6+1^5}}{(9 + 7)^{2 \times 3 + 0}} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (8^{6+1-5}))}{((9 + 7) \times (2 + 30))} := \frac{(4 \times (8 + (6 + (1^5))))}{((9 - (7 - 2)) \times 30)} := \frac{(4 \times (8 + (6 + (1 - 5))))}{((9 + 7) \times (2 + (3 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (8 + (6 + 15)))}{(9 - (7 - 230))} := \frac{4^{8-6+1 \times 5}}{(((9 + 7) \times 2)^3 + 0)} := \frac{4^{8-6+1^5}}{((9 + 7) \times (2^3 + 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{4^{8-6 \times 1^5}}{(9 - 7)^{2+3} + 0} := \frac{4^{8-6-1^5}}{(9 + (7 - (2^3 + 0)))} := \frac{(4 + ((8 - (6 + 1)) \times 5))}{(9 \times (7 - (2 + (3 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + ((8 \times (6 - 1)) + 5))}{(97 - (2 - (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 + ((8 \times (6 - 1)) - 5))}{(9 + (72 - (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 + ((8 \times 6) - (1 + 5)))}{(97 - (2 + (3 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + ((8 \times 6) + 15))}{(9 + ((7 - 2)^3 + 0))} := \frac{(4 + ((8 - 6) \times 15))}{((9 \times 7) + (2 + (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 + (8 - (6 - (1 \times 5))))}{(9 + (7 + (2 \times (3 - 0))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 - (6 \times (1 - 5))))}{(9 \times (7 - (2 - (3 - 0))))} := \frac{(4 + (8 - (6 \times (1^5))))}{((9 - (7 - 2)) \times (3 - 0))} := \frac{(4 + (8 - (6 + (1 - 5))))}{(9 + ((7 \times 2) - (3 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 - (6 - 15)))}{((9 + (7 - 2)) \times (3 - 0))} := \frac{(4 + (8 \times (6 - (1^5))))}{(9 + ((7^2) + 30))} := \frac{(4 + (8 \times (6 + (1 - 5))))}{((9 \times 7) - (23 - 0))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + ((6 - 1) \times 5)))}{(97 - (23 - 0))} := \frac{(4 + (8 + (6 - (1 \times 5))))}{(9 + ((7 \times 2) + (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 + (8 + (6 - (1 - 5))))}{(9 + (7 - (2 - 30)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + (6 \times (1 \times 5))))}{(9 + (72 + (3 - 0)))} := \frac{(4 + (8 + (6 \times (1 + 5))))}{((9 \times (7 \times 2)) - 30)} := \frac{(4 + (8 + (6 \times (1^5))))}{(9 + ((7 + 2) \times (3 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + (6 + (1 \times 5))))}{((9 - 7) \times (23 - 0))} := \frac{(4 + (8 + (6 + (1 - 5))))}{(9 + ((7^2) - 30))} := \frac{(4 + (8 + (61 + 5)))}{(9 + ((7^2) \times (3 - 0)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (861 + 5))}{((9 + (7^2)) \times 30)} := \frac{(48 - (6 - (1^5)))}{((9 \times 7) + (23 - 0))} := \frac{(48 - (6 - (1 - 5)))}{(9 + (7 + (2 \times 30)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(48 - (6 + 15))}{(9 \times (7 + (2 - (3 - 0))))} := \frac{(48 \times (6 - (1 - 5)))}{((9 + 7) \times (2 \times 30))} := \frac{(48 \times (6 + 15))}{(9 \times (7 \times (2 + 30)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(48 + (6 \times (1^5)))}{(9 \times (7 + (2 + (3 - 0))))} := \frac{(486 \times (1 + 5))}{((9 + (7 + 2))^3 + 0)} := \frac{(486 + 15)}{(972 + 30)} \\ &:= \frac{(486 - 15)}{(972 - 30)} \end{aligned}$$

3.64 68 Equivalent Blocks

► **10579**
84632

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(((1 - (0 - 5)) \times 7) + 9)}{(8 \times (46 + (3 + 2)))} := \frac{(((1 - (0 - 5)) \times 7) - 9)}{(8 \times ((4 \times 6) + (3^2)))} := \frac{(((1^{05}) + 7) \times 9)}{(8 \times (4 \times ((6 + 3) \times 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(((1^{05}) + 7)^9)}{((8 + (4 \times 6))^{3 \times 2})} := \frac{(((1 - (0 - (5 \times 7))) \times 9)}{(8 \times (4 \times ((6 + 3)^2)))} := \frac{(((1 - (0 - 5)) \times (7 \times 9))}{(84 \times (6 \times (3 \times 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(((1 - (0 - 5)) \times (7 + 9))}{((8 - 4) \times (6 \times 32))} := \frac{((1^{05}) \times (7 \times 9))}{(84 \times (6 \times (3 - 2)))} := \frac{(((1^{05}) \times (7 + 9))}{(8 + (4 \times (6 \times (3 + 2))))} \\ &:= \frac{((1^{05}) + (7 \times 9))}{8^{4-6+3+2}} := \frac{((1^{05}) + (7 + 9))}{(8 + ((4^{6-3}) \times 2))} := \frac{(((1 + (0 - (5 - 7))) \times 9)}{((8 - 4) \times (6 \times (3^2)))} \\ &:= \frac{((10 \times (5 + 7)) + 9)}{(8 + (4^{6-3+2}))} := \frac{((10 \times 5) - (7 + 9))}{(8 \times (4 + (6 \times (3 + 2))))} := \frac{((10 \times 5) - (7 - 9))}{(8 \times (46 + (3 \times 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - ((5 \times 7) + 9)))}{(8 \times (46 - (3 - 2)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - ((5 + 7) \times 9)))}{((8 - 4) \times ((6^3) + 2))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 - (7 - 9))))}{8^{(4-6+3) \times 2}} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 \times (7 \times 9))))}{((8 - 4) \times 632)} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 \times (7 + 9))))}{((8 + 4) \times (6 \times (3^2)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 + (7 \times 9))))}{(8 \times (4 + (63 + 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 + (7 + 9))))}{(8 \times (4 + ((6 + 3) \times 2)))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 + (7 - 9))))}{(8 + (4 \times (6 \times (3 - 2))))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (5 + 79)))}{(8 \times (4 + ((6 + 3)^2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (0 - (57 \times 9)))}{((8^4) + ((6 \times 3) - 2))} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (57 + 9)))}{((84 \times 6) + 32)} := \frac{(1 - (0 - (57 - 9)))}{(8 \times ((4 + (6 - 3))^2))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 - (0 \times (5 - 79)))}{8^{4+6-3^2}} := \frac{(1 - (0 - 579))}{(8 + 4632)} := \frac{(1 \times ((0 - (5 - 7))^9))}{8^4 \times (6 - 3 - 2)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times ((0 \times 5) - (7 - 9)))}{(8 - (4 - (6 + (3 \times 2))))} := \frac{(1 \times ((0 \times 57) + 9))}{(8 \times (4 + (6 - (3 - 2))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 - ((5 - 7) \times 9)))}{((8 + (4^{6-3})) \times 2)} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 - (5 - (7 \times 9))))}{(8 \times (4 + (6 \times (3^2))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 - (5 \times (7 - 9))))}{(8 \times (4 + (6 \times (3 - 2))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 - (5 - 79)))}{(8 \times ((4 \times (6 \times 3)) + 2))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((5 \times 7) + 9)))}{(8 \times (4 \times (6 + (3 + 2))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((5 \times 7) - 9)))}{(8 \times ((4 + (6 + 3)) \times 2))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((5 + 7) \times 9)))}{(8 + (4 \times ((6^3) - 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + ((5 + 7)^9))}{((8^4) \times (6^3))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (5 - (7 - 9))))}{(8 \times (4 - (6 - (3^2))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (5 \times (7 \times 9))))}{(84 \times (6 \times (3 + 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (5 \times (7 + 9))))}{(8 \times (4 \times ((6 \times 3) + 2)))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (5 + (7 - 9))))}{(8 \times (4 - (6 - (3 + 2))))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (57 \times 9)))}{(8 + (4^6 \times (3 - 2)))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 \times (0 + (57 + 9)))}{(8 \times ((4^{6-3}) + 2))} := \frac{(1 \times (0 + (57 - 9)))}{(8 \times (4 \times (6 + (3 \times 2))))} := \frac{(1 + (0 - ((5 - 7) \times 9)))}{(8 \times (4 + (6 + (3^2))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (5 - (7 \times 9))))}{((84 \times 6) - 32)} := \frac{(1 + (0 - (5 - (7 + 9))))}{(84 + (6 + (3 \times 2)))} := \frac{(1 + (0 - (5 \times (7 - 9))))}{(8 \times (4 + (6 + (3 - 2))))} \\ &:= \frac{(1 + (0 - (5 - 79)))}{((84 + (6^3)) \times 2)} := \frac{(10 - ((5 - 7) \times 9))}{(8 + (4 \times (6 \times (3^2))))} := \frac{(10 - (5 \times (7 - 9)))}{(8 + (4 \times (6 + 32)))} \\ &:= \frac{(10 \times ((5 \times 7) + 9))}{(8 \times ((4 + (6^3)) \times 2))} := \frac{(10 \times ((5 \times 7) - 9))}{(8 \times (4 \times (63 + 2)))} := \frac{(10 \times (5 - (7 - 9)))}{(8 \times ((4 \times (6 \times 3)) - 2))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(10 \times (5 \times (7 + 9)))}{((8 + (4 \times (6 \times 3)))^2)} &:= \frac{(10 \times (5 + (7 + 9)))}{(84 \times ((6 \times 3) + 2))} &:= \frac{(10 \times (5 + (7 - 9)))}{(8 \times (4 - (6 - 32)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 + ((5 \times 7) + 9))}{(8 - ((4 - (6^3)) \times 2))} &:= \frac{(10 + ((5 \times 7) - 9))}{(8 \times (4 \times ((6 - 3)^2)))} &:= \frac{(10 + (5 \times (7 + 9)))}{(8 \times ((4 + 6) \times (3^2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(10 + (5 + (7 \times 9)))}{(8 \times (46 + 32))} &:= \frac{(10 + (5 + (7 - 9)))}{(8 \times (4 + ((6 - 3)^2)))} &:= \frac{(105 - (7 \times 9))}{(8 \times (4 + (6 + 32)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(105 - (7 - 9))}{((8 - 4) \times ((6^3) - 2))} &:= \frac{(105 + (7 \times 9))}{(84 \times ((6 \times 3) - 2))} &
 \end{aligned}$$

► **34851**
69702

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((3 - (4 - 8)) \times 5) - 1)}{((6 \times 9) - (7 \times (0 - 2)))} &:= \frac{(((3^4) - 8) \times (5 - 1))}{((6 \times (97 - 0)) + 2)} &:= \frac{(((3 + (4 \times 8)) \times 5) - 1)}{(6 \times (9 + (7^{02})))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((3 + (4 + 8)) \times 5) + 1)}{((69 + (7 - 0)) \times 2)} &:= \frac{(((3 + 4) \times 8) + (5 \times 1))}{((6 \times 9) + (70 - 2))} &:= \frac{((3 \times ((4 \times 8) - 5)) + 1)}{(6 + ((9 + 70) \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (4 \times (8 - 5))) + 1)}{(69 + (7 + (0 - 2)))} &:= \frac{((3 \times (4 \times 8)) + (5 - 1))}{(6 - (97 \times (0 - 2)))} &:= \frac{((3 \times (4 + (8 - 5))) + 1)}{((6 + (9 + (7 - 0))) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (4 + 8)) - (5 + 1))}{(69 - (7 - (0 - 2)))} &:= \frac{((3 \times (4 + 8)) - (5 - 1))}{(6 + (9 + (7^{02})))} &:= \frac{((3 \times 4) - (8 - (5 - 1)))}{((6 - (9 - (7 - 0)))^2)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times 4) + (85 \times 1))}{((6 \times 9) + (70 \times 2))} &:= \frac{((3 \times 4) + (85 - 1))}{(6 \times ((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 2))} &:= \frac{((3 \times 48) - (5 \times 1))}{((69 + 70) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3^4) - (8 \times (5 - 1)))}{((6 \times (9 + (7 - 0))) + 2)} &:= \frac{((3^4) - (8 + (5 - 1)))}{(6 \times (9 - (7 \times (0 - 2))))} &:= \frac{((3^4) - (8 - 51))}{(((6 \times 9) + 70) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{((34 \times (8 - 5)) + 1)}{((6 + (97 - 0)) \times 2)} &:= \frac{(3 - ((4 - 8) \times (5 \times 1)))}{(6 - (9 - (7^{02})))} &:= \frac{(3 - ((4 - 8) \times (5 + 1)))}{(6 \times (9 - (7 \times (0 \times 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (4 - ((8 \times 5) - 1)))}{(69 + (7 - (0 \times 2)))} &:= \frac{(3 - (4 - (8 - (5 \times 1))))}{(6 - (9 - (7 - (0 \times 2))))} &:= \frac{(3 - (4 - (8 - (5 + 1))))}{(6 - (9 - (7 + (0 - 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (4 - (8 \times (5 \times 1))))}{(69 + (7 - (0 - 2)))} &:= \frac{(3 - (4 - (8 \times (5 - 1))))}{(3 - (4 + (8 - 51)))} &:= \frac{(3 - (4 - (8 + (5 \times 1))))}{(6 + (9 + (7 - (0 - 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (4 - (85 + 1)))}{((6 + (9 + 70)) \times 2)} &:= \frac{(3 - (4 + (8 - 51)))}{(6 \times (9 + (7 + (0 - 2))))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (((4 + 8) \times 5) + 1))}{(6 \times ((9 \times (7 - 0)) - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (4 \times (8 - (5 \times 1))))}{((6^9 - 7 + 0) \times 2)} &:= \frac{(3 \times (4 \times (8 - (5 - 1))))}{(6 \times (9 \times (70 - 2)))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (4^{8-5+1}))}{(6 \times (9 - (7 - (0 \times 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (4 + ((8 \times 5) + 1)))}{(6 \times (9 \times (7 - (0 \times 2))))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (4 + (8 - (5 \times 1))))}{(6 \times (9 + (7 - (0 \times 2))))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (4 + (8 - (5 + 1))))}{(6 \times ((9 + (7 - 0))^2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (4 + (8 + (5 + 1))))}{(6 \times (9 + (7 - (0 - 2))))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (4 + (8 + 51)))}{((6 - 9) \times (7 \times (0 - 2)))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (48 + 51))}{6^{9-7+0 \times 2}} \\
 &:= \frac{3^{4-8+5 \times 1}}{(6 \times (9 + (7 - (0 - 2))))} &:= \frac{(3 + (((4 + 8) \times 5) + 1))}{(6 \times (9 \times (7 - (0 \times 2))))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (48 + 51))}{(6 \times (97 - (0 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 - (9 - (7 - (0 - 2))))}{(3 + ((4 + 8) \times (5 \times 1)))} &:= \frac{(6 - ((9 - 70) \times 2))}{(3 + ((48 \times 5) - 1))} &:= \frac{((69 - (7 - 0)) \times 2)}{(3 + (4 - (8 - (5 \times 1))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 \times 9) + (70 + 2))}{(3 + (4 - (8 - (5 + 1))))} &:= \frac{((6 + (9 + (7 - 0)))^2)}{(3 + (4 \times (8 - (5 - 1))))} &:= \frac{(6 + (9 - (7 - (0 \times 2))))}{(3 + (4 \times (8 \times (5 + 1))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 + (9 - (7 + (0 - 2))))}{(3 + (4 \times (8 \times (5 - 1))))} &:= \frac{((6^9 - 7 + 0) + 2)}{(3 + (4 \times (8 + (5 + 1))))} &:= \frac{(6 \times ((9 \times (7 - 0)) + 2))}{3 + 4^{8-5 \times 1}} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 + ((9 + (7 - 0))^2))}{(3 + (4 + (8 - (5 \times 1))))} &:= \frac{(69 + (7^{02}))}{(3 + (4 + (8 - (5 - 1))))} &:= \frac{((6 - (9 - 70)) \times 2)}{(3 + (4 + (8 \times (5 \times 1))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 + (9 + (7 + (0 - 2))))}{(6 + (9 + (7 - (0 \times 2))))} &:= \frac{(6 + (9 + (7 - (0 \times 2))))}{(6 + (9 + (7 - (0 \times 2))))} &:= \frac{((6 \times (9 + (7 - 0))) - 2)}{(6 \times (9 + (7 - 0))) - 2}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(3 + (4 + (8 + (5 \times 1))))}{((6 \times 9) + (7 \times (0 - 2)))} := \frac{(3 + (4 + (8 + 51)))}{(6 - (9 \times (7 \times (0 - 2))))} := \frac{(3 + (4 + (85 - 1)))}{((6 - 97) \times (0 - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (48 \times (5 \times 1)))}{(6 \times (9 \times (7 - (0 - 2))))} := \frac{(3 + (48 \times (5 + 1)))}{(6 \times (97 - (0 \times 2)))} := \frac{(3 + (48 + (5 + 1)))}{((6 - (9 \times 7)) \times (0 - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{3 + 485 + 1}{6 + 970 + 2} := \frac{3 + 485 - 1}{6 + 970 - 2} := \frac{3 + 4851}{6 + 9702} \\
 &:= \frac{3485 + 1}{6970 + 2} := \frac{3485 - 1}{6970 - 2}
 \end{aligned}$$

► **48531**
97062

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((4 + 8) \times 5) - 31)}{9 + 7^{0 \times 6 + 2}} := \frac{(((4 \times (8 - (5 + 3))) + 1))}{(9 - (7 - (0 \times 62)))} := \frac{(((4 \times (8 \times (5 \times 3))) + 1))}{(970 - (6 + 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((4 \times (8 \times (5 \times 3))) - 1))}{(970 - (6 \times 2))} := \frac{(((4 \times (8 \times (5 - 3))) - 1))}{(9 \times (7 \times ((0 \times 6) + 2)))} := \frac{(((4 \times (8 \times 5)) - (3 - 1))}{((9 + 70) \times (6 - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((4 \times (8 + (5 \times 3))) - 1))}{((97 + (0 - 6)) \times 2)} := \frac{(((4 \times (8 + (5 - 3))) - 1))}{(9 + (7 - (0 - 62)))} := \frac{(((4 \times (8 - 5)) - (3 + 1))}{(9 + (7 - (0 \times 62)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((4 \times (85 + 3)) - 1))}{(9 \times (70 + (6 + 2)))} := \frac{(((4 \times 8) - (5^{3-1}))}{(9 - (7 + (0 - (6 \times 2))))} := \frac{(((4 \times 85) + (3 \times 1))}{((9 \times (70 + 6)) + 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times 85) - 31)}{((9 \times 70) - (6 \times 2))} := \frac{((4^{8-5}) - (3 - 1))}{((9 - (7 - 0)) \times 62)} := \frac{((4^{8-5}) \times (3 - 1))}{((9 + (7 - (0 \times 6)))^2)} \\
 &:= \frac{((4^{8-5})^{3+1})}{(((9 + (7 - 0))^6) \times 2)} := \frac{((4^{8-5}) - 31)}{(((9 - (7 - 0))^6) + 2)} := \frac{((4 + (8 + 5)) \times (3 \times 1))}{((9 - (7 \times (0 - 6))) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 + (8 + 5))^{3-1})}{((9 \times (70 - 6)) + 2)} := \frac{((4 + 8) \times (5 \times (3 \times 1)))}{(9 \times ((7 \times (0 + 6)) - 2))} := \frac{((4 + 8) \times (53 \times 1))}{(((9 \times 70) + 6) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 + 8) \times (53 - 1))}{(((9 \times 70) - 6) \times 2)} := \frac{((48 \times 5) - (3 + 1))}{(((9 + 70) \times 6) - 2)} := \frac{((48 \times 5) - (3 - 1))}{(((9 + 70) \times 6) + 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{((48 \times 5) + (3 - 1))}{((9 + (7 - (0 - 6)))^2)} := \frac{(4 - (8 - (5 \times (3 + 1))))}{((9 + (7 - (0 \times 6))) \times 2)} := \frac{(4 - (8 - (5 \times (3 - 1))))}{(9 + (7 + (0 - (6 - 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (8 - (5 + (3 \times 1))))}{(9 + (7 + (0 - (6 + 2))))} := \frac{(4 - (8 - (5 + (3 - 1))))}{(9 - (7 + (0 - (6 - 2))))} := \frac{(4 - (8 - (5 + 31)))}{(9 - (7 + (0 - 62)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (8 - (53 \times 1)))}{(((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 6) + 2)} := \frac{(4 - (8 - (53 + 1)))}{((9 + (7 + (0 - 6)))^2)} := \frac{(4 - (8 + (5 - 31)))}{((9 + (7 - (0 - 6))) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times ((8 \times 5) + 31))}{((9 \times 70) - 62)} := \frac{(4 \times ((8^{5-3}) - 1))}{(9 \times (7 \times (0 + (6 + 2))))} := \frac{(4 \times ((8^5)^3 \times 1))}{(((9 + (7 - 0))^6)^2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (8 \times (5 - (3 \times 1))))}{(((9 - (7 - 0))^6) \times 2)} := \frac{(4 \times (8 \times (5 - (3 - 1))))}{((9 + (7 - 0)) \times (6 \times 2))} := \frac{(4 \times (8 \times (5 + (3 + 1))))}{((9 + (7 - 0)) \times (6^2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (8^{5-3+1}))}{(((9 - (7 - 0))^6)^2)} := \frac{(4 \times (8 + (5 - (3 + 1))))}{(9 \times (70 - 62))} := \frac{(4 \times (8 + (5 \times (3 - 1))))}{(((9 - (7 - 0)) \times 6)^2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + ((8 \times 5) + (3 \times 1)))}{(((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 6) - 2)} := \frac{(4 + ((8 \times 53) + 1))}{((9 + (70 \times 6)) \times 2)} := \frac{(4 + ((8^{5-3}) + 1))}{(((9 \times (7 - 0)) + 6) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + ((8^5) - (3 + 1)))}{((9 + (7 - 0))^{6-2})} := \frac{(4 + ((8 - 5) \times 31))}{(97 \times ((0 \times 6) + 2))} := \frac{(4 + ((8 - 5)^3 \times 1))}{(((9 - (7 - 0))^6) - 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 - (5 - (3 \times 1))))}{(9 + (7 - (0 - (6 - 2))))} := \frac{(4 + (8 - (5 - (3 - 1))))}{(9 \times ((7 + (0 - 6)) \times 2))} := \frac{(4 + (8 - (5 \times (3 - 1))))}{(9 + (7 + (0 - (6 \times 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 - (5 + (3 - 1))))}{(9 - (7 + (0 - (6 + 2))))} := \frac{(4 + (8 \times (5 + 31)))}{((97 \times (0 + 6)) + 2)} := \frac{(4 + (8^{5-3-1}))}{(9 + (7 - (0 - (6 + 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8^{5-3+1}))}{(970 + 62)} := \frac{(4 + (8 + ((5 \times 3) - 1)))}{(9 + (7 - (0 - (6^2))))} := \frac{(4 + (8 + (5 - (3 \times 1))))}{(9 + (7 - (0 - (6 \times 2))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + (5 + (3 - 1))))}{(9 - (7 + (0 - (6^2))))} := \frac{(4 + (85 - (3 + 1)))}{((9 + (70 + 6)) \times 2)} := \frac{(48 + (5^{3-1}))}{((9 + (70 - 6)) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(48 + (5 + (3 + 1)))}{(((9 \times (7 - 0)) - 6) \times 2)} := \frac{(485 - (3 - 1))}{(970 - (6 - 2))} := \frac{(485 \times (3 + 1))}{(485 \times (6 - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(485 + (3 + 1))}{(970 + (6 + 2))} := \frac{(485 + (3 - 1))}{(970 + (6 - 2))} := \frac{(4853 + 1)}{(9706 + 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4853 - 1)}{(9706 - 2)} := \frac{(485 - 31)}{(970 - 62)}
 \end{aligned}$$

► **48651**
97302

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((4 \times 8) + 6) \times 5) - 1}{(9 \times (7 \times (3 \times (0 + 2))))} := \frac{(((4 - (8 - 6)) \times 5) - 1)}{(9 \times (7 - (3 - (0 - 2))))} := \frac{(((4 + 8) \times 6) - (5 + 1))}{((9 \times 7) + (3 - 0)) \times 2} \\
 &:= \frac{(((4 + 86) \times 5) + 1)}{(9 - (7 - (30^2)))} := \frac{(((4 \times ((8 - 6)^5)) - 1)}{((97 + 30) \times 2)} := \frac{(((4 \times (8 - (6 - 5))) + 1)}{(((9 - 7) \times 30) - 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((4 \times (8 - (6 - 5))) - 1)}{(9 \times (7 - (3 + (0 - 2))))} := \frac{(((4 \times (8 \times (6 - 5))) + 1)}{((9 \times 7) + (3 - (0 \times 2)))} := \frac{(((4 \times (8 \times (6 - 5))) - 1)}{(9 - (7 - (30 \times 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((4 \times (8 + 6)) - (5 \times 1))}{(97 + (3 - (0 - 2)))} := \frac{(((4 \times (8 + 6)) - (5 + 1))}{(97 + (3 - (0 \times 2)))} := \frac{(((4 \times (8 + 6)) - 51)}{(9 + (7 + (3 \times (0 - 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((4 \times (8 + 65)) - 1)}{(97 \times (3 \times (0 + 2)))} := \frac{(((4 \times (8 - 6)) - (5 \times 1))}{((9 - 7) \times (3 - (0 \times 2)))} := \frac{(((4 \times 8) + (6 - (5 - 1)))}{((9 \times 7) + (3 - (0 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4^{8-6}) + 51)}{((97 - 30) \times 2)} := \frac{(((4 + (8 + 6)) \times (5 \times 1))}{(9 \times ((7 + (3 - 0)) \times 2))} := \frac{(((4 + (8 - 6)) \times (5 \times 1))}{((9 + (7 \times (3 - 0))) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 + 86) \times (5 \times 1))}{(9 \times ((7 + (3 - 0))^2))} := \frac{(4 - (8 - ((6 \times 5) - 1)))}{((9 + 7) \times (3 - 0)) + 2} := \frac{(4 - (8 - (6 \times 51)))}{(4 - (8 - (6 + 51)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 + 7^{3-02})}{(4 - (8 - (65 - 1)))} := \frac{((9 - 7) \times (3 \times (0 + 2)))}{(4 - (8 \times (6 - (5 + 1))))} := \frac{(97 + (3^{02}))}{(4 - (8 + (6 - 51)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((9 - 7) \times (30 \times 2))}{(4 \times (((8 - 6) \times 5) + 1))} := \frac{(9 - (7 + (3 \times (0 - 2))))}{(4 \times ((8 + 6) \times (5 - 1)))} := \frac{(9 + (73 - (0 \times 2)))}{(4 \times (8 - (6 - (5 \times 1))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((9 \times (7 + (3 - 0))) - 2)}{((9 \times 7) \times (30 - 2))} := \frac{((9 + 7) \times (30 - 2))}{(4 \times (8 \times (6 - (5 - 1))))} := \frac{((9 - 7) \times (30 - 2))}{(4 \times (8 \times (6 \times (5 + 1))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (8 - (6 - (5 - 1))))}{(9 + (7 + (30 + 2)))} := \frac{((9 - 73) \times (0 - 2))}{((9 - 73) \times (0 - 2))} := \frac{(((9 + 7) \times (3 - 0))^2)}{(4 \times (8^{6-5 \times 1}))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (8 \times (6 + (5 \times 1))))}{((9 + (7^3 + 0)) \times 2)} := \frac{(4 \times (8 \times (65 - 1)))}{(9 + 7)^{3+0 \times 2}} := \frac{(4 \times (8^{6-5 \times 1}))}{((9 - (7 - 30)) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{4 \times 8^{6-5+1}}{(9 - 7)^{3^{02}}} := \frac{(4 \times (8 + (6 - (5 \times 1))))}{(9 \times (7 + (3 + (0 - 2))))} := \frac{(4 \times (8 + (6 - (5 - 1))))}{(9 + (73 + (0 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (8 + (6 \times (5 \times 1))))}{(9 - (7 - 302))} := \frac{(4 \times (8 + (6 \times (5 + 1))))}{9 + 7^{3+0 \times 2}} := \frac{(4 \times (8 + (6 + (5 - 1))))}{(9 \times (7 + (3^{02})))} \\
 &:= \frac{4^{8-6+5-1}}{(((9 + 7)^3 + 0) \times 2)} := \frac{(4 + (((8 - 6) \times 5) + 1))}{(9 + (7 \times (3 - (0 \times 2))))} := \frac{(4 + ((8 \times (6 + 5)) + 1))}{(((9 \times 7) + 30) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + ((8 \times 6) - (5 \times 1)))}{(97 - (3 - (0 \times 2)))} := \frac{(4 + ((8 \times 6) - (5 + 1)))}{((9 + (7 + 30)) \times 2)} := \frac{(4 + ((8 - 6) \times (5 + 1)))}{(9 + ((7 \times (3 - 0)) + 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 - (6 - (5 \times 1))))}{(9 + (7 - (3 \times (0 - 2))))} := \frac{(4 + (8 - (6 + (5 \times 1))))}{9 - 7^{3-02}} := \frac{(4 + (8 - (6 + (5 - 1))))}{(((9 - 7) \times (3 - 0)) - 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 \times (6 + (5 + 1))))}{((97 + (3 - 0)) \times 2)} := \frac{(4 + (8^{6-5 \times 1}))}{((9 - (7 \times 3)) \times (0 - 2))} := \frac{(4 + (8 + (6 - (5 \times 1))))}{((9 + (7 - (3 - 0))) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + (6 - (5 - 1))))}{(9 + ((7 \times (3 - 0)) - 2))} := \frac{(4 + (8 + (6 \times (5 \times 1))))}{(9 + (73 - (0 - 2)))} := \frac{(4 + (8 + (6 \times (5 + 1))))}{(97 - (3 + (0 - 2)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + (6 + (5 \times 1))))}{(((9 + 7) \times (3 - 0)) - 2)} := \frac{(4 + (8 + (6 + (5 - 1))))}{(9 + (7 \times (3 - (0 - 2))))} := \frac{(4 + (86 + (5 - 1)))}{((97 - (3 - 0)) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(48 - ((6 \times 5) + 1))}{(9 - (7 - (30 + 2)))} := \frac{(48 - ((6 \times 5) - 1))}{((9 \times (7 - (3 - 0))) + 2)} := \frac{(48 - (6 \times (5 \times 1)))}{(9 \times (7 - (3 - (0 \times 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(48 - (6 + (5 - 1)))}{(9 + (7 + (30 \times 2)))} := \frac{(48 \times (6 + (5 - 1)))}{((9 + 7) \times (30 \times 2))} := \frac{(48 + (6 - (5 \times 1)))}{(97 + (3 + (0 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4865 + 1)}{(9730 + 2)} := \frac{(4865 - 1)}{(9730 - 2)}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.65 69 Equivalent Blocks

► 27093
54186

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((2 \times (7 - 0)) + 9) \times 3)}{(((5 \times (4 - 1)) + 8) \times 6)} := \frac{(((2 + (7 - 0))^9) \times 3)}{(((5 + 4) \times (1 + 8)) \times 6)} := \frac{(((2 + 70) \times 9) - 3)}{(5 \times ((4 - 1) \times 86))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((2 - 7) \times (0 - 9)) + 3)}{(5 + (4 + (1 + 86)))} := \frac{(((2 - (7 \times (0 - 9))) \times 3)}{(5 \times ((4 \times 18) + 6))} := \frac{(((2 - (7 + (0 - 9))) \times 3)}{(5 + (4 + (1 + (8 + 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 - (7 + (0 - 9)))^3)}{((5 \times 4) + (18 \times 6))} := \frac{((2 \times (7 - (0 \times 9))) + 3)}{((5 \times (4 \times 1)) + (8 + 6))} := \frac{((2 \times (7 - (0 \times 9))) - 3)}{(5 + (4 - (1 - (8 + 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (7 - (0 - 9))) + 3)}{(((5 + (4 - 1)) \times 8) + 6)} := \frac{((2 \times (7 - (0 - 9))) - 3)}{(5 + (4 + (1 + (8 \times 6))))} := \frac{((2 \times (7 \times (0 + 9))) - 3)}{((5 + (4 \times (1 + 8))) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times 70) - 93)}{(5 + (4 - (1 - 86)))} := \frac{((2^{7+0 \times 9}) + 3)}{(((5 - (4 - 1))^8) + 6)} := \frac{((2^{7+0 \times 9}) - 3)}{((5^{4-1}) \times (8 - 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^7 + 0) \times (9 - 3))}{(((5 - (4 - 1))^8) \times 6)} := \frac{((2^7 + 0) + (9 + 3))}{(5 \times (4 \times (1 \times (8 + 6))))} := \frac{((2 + (7 - (0 \times 9))) \times 3)}{((5 + (4 \times (1^8))) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + (7 - (0 - 9))) \times 3)}{((5 + (4 + (1 + 8))) \times 6)} := \frac{((2 + (7 - 0)) \times (9 + 3))}{((54 - 18) \times 6)} := \frac{((2 + (7 - 0)) \times 93)}{((2 + (70 - 9)) \times 3)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((5^4) - (1 - 8)) \times 6)}{((2 - 7) \times (0 - (9 \times 3)))} := \frac{((27 \times (0 + 9))^3)}{(54 \times ((1 + 8)^6))} := \frac{((27 \times (0 + 9)) + 3)}{((54 \times (1 + 8)) + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{((27 \times (0 + 9)) - 3)}{(5 \times (4 \times (18 + 6)))} := \frac{(2 - ((7 \times (0 \times 9)) - 3))}{(5 + (4 + (1^{86})))} := \frac{(2 - ((7 + (0 - 9)) \times 3))}{(5 - (4 - (1 + (8 + 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (7 \times (0 - (9 + 3))))}{((5 - (4 - 1)) \times 86)} := \frac{(2 - (7 \times (0 - (9 - 3))))}{(5 - (4 - (1 + 86)))} := \frac{(2 - (7 \times (0 \times 93)))}{(5 - (4 - (1 + (8 - 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (7 + (0 - (9 \times 3))))}{(5 + (41 - (8 - 6)))} := \frac{(2 - (7 + (0 - (9 + 3))))}{(5 - (4 + (1 - (8 + 6))))} := \frac{(2 - (7 + (0 - (9 - 3))))}{(5 - (4 - (1^{86})))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (70 - 93))}{(5 - (4 - (1 + (8 \times 6))))} := \frac{(2 \times ((7 \times (0 + 9)) - 3))}{(5 \times (4 \times (18 - 6)))} := \frac{(2 \times (7 - ((0 \times 9) - 3)))}{(5 \times (4 \times (1 \times (8 - 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 - (4 - (1 + (8 \times 6))))}{(2 \times (7 - (0 - (9 - 3))))} := \frac{(5 \times (4 \times (18 - 6)))}{(2 \times (7 - (0 \times 93)))} := \frac{(5 \times (4 \times (1 \times (8 - 6))))}{(2 \times (7 - (0 - 93)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(54 - (1 \times (8 - 6)))}{(2 \times (7 \times (0 + (9 \times 3))))} := \frac{((5 - (4 - 1)) \times (8 + 6))}{(2 \times (7 \times (0 + (9 - 3))))} := \frac{((5 \times (4 \times 1))^{8-6})}{2^{7+0 \times 9-3}} \\
 &:= \frac{(54 \times (1 \times (8 + 6)))}{(2 + ((7 - (0 - 9)) \times 3))} := \frac{(((5 \times (4 \times 1)) + 8) \times 6)}{(2 + (7 - (0 - (9 \times 3))))} := \frac{(5 + (41 - (8 + 6)))}{(2 + (7 - (0 - (9 + 3))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 + (4 + 1))^{8-6})}{(2 + (7 - (0 - (9 - 3))))} := \frac{(((5 \times (4 \times 1)) - 8) \times 6)}{(2 + (7 - (0 \times 93)))} := \frac{(((5 \times (4 - 1)) - 8) \times 6)}{(2 + (7 + ((0 \times 9) - 3)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times (4 + (1 \times (8 - 6))))}{(2 + (7 + (0 - (9 - 3))))} := \frac{((5 + (4 \times 1)) \times (8 - 6))}{(2 + (70 - (9 \times 3)))} := \frac{(5 + (4 + (1 + (8 - 6))))}{(2 + (70 - (9 + 3)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (4 - (1 + (8 - 6))))}{(5 + (4 - (1 \times (8 + 6))))} := \frac{(5 \times (4 + (1 \times (8 + 6))))}{(5 \times (4 \times ((1^8) \times 6))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(2 + (70 - (9 - 3)))}{(5 + (41 + 86))} &:= \frac{(2 + (70 + (9 \times 3)))}{((5 - (4 \times (1 - 8))) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(2 + (70 + (9 - 3)))}{(((5 + 4) \times 18) - 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (70 + 93))}{(5 \times ((4 \times 18) - 6))} &:= \frac{(27 - ((0 \times 9) - 3))}{(5 \times (4 \times (1 + (8 - 6))))} &:= \frac{(27 - (0 - (9 + 3)))}{(((5 + (4 \times 1)) \times 8) + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(27 - (0 - (9 - 3)))}{((5 \times (4 + (1 \times 8))) + 6)} &:= \frac{(27 \times ((0 \times 9) + 3))}{((5 + (4 + 18)) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(27 \times (0 + (9 + 3)))}{(54 \times (18 - 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(27 \times (0 + (9 - 3)))}{((5 + (41 + 8)) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(27 + ((0 \times 9) - 3))}{(5 - (4 + (1 - (8 \times 6))))} &:= \frac{(270 + 9^3)}{((5 + (41 \times 8)) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{270 - 93}{5 \times 4 \times 18 - 6} &:= \frac{2709 + 3}{5418 + 6} &:= \frac{2709 - 3}{5418 - 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

► $\frac{29307}{58614}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((2 - (9 \times 3)) \times (0 - 7))}{((5^{8-6}) \times 14)} &:= \frac{((2 - (9 + 3)) \times (0 - 7))}{(5 \times (8 + (6 + 14)))} &:= \frac{((2 - (9 - 3)) \times (0 - 7))}{((5 \times (8 + 6)) - 14)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (9 - (3 - 0))) + 7)}{(58 - (6 + 14))} &:= \frac{((2 \times (9 - (3 - 0))) - 7)}{(5 \times (8 - (6 \times (1^4))))} &:= \frac{((2 \times (9 \times (3 - 0))) - 7)}{(5 + (86 - (1 - 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (9^3 + 0)) + 7)}{(586 \times (1 + 4))} &:= \frac{((2 \times (9 + (3 - 0))) + 7)}{(5 - (8 - (61 + 4)))} &:= \frac{((2 \times (9 + (3 - 0))) - 7)}{(58 - (6 \times (1 \times 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (9 + 30)) + 7)}{(5 \times ((8 \times 6) - 14))} &:= \frac{((2 \times (9 + 30)) - 7)}{(58 + (6 \times 14))} &:= \frac{((2 \times 9) + (30 - 7))}{(58 + (6 \times (1 \times 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{2^{9-3+0} \times 7}{((58 + 6) \times 14)} &:= \frac{((2^9) - 307)}{(5 \times (86 - (1 \times 4)))} &:= \frac{((2 + (9 + (3 - 0))) \times 7)}{((5 \times (8 \times (6 - 1))) - 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + 9) \times (3 - (0 - 7)))}{(5 \times ((8 \times (6 \times 1)) - 4))} &:= \frac{((29 - (3 - 0)) \times 7)}{((5 + (86 \times 1)) \times 4)} &:= \frac{((2 - 9) \times (3 \times (0 - 7)))}{((58 \times (6 - 1)) + 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{((29 \times (3 - 0)) + 7)}{(((5 \times 8) + (6 + 1)) \times 4)} &:= \frac{((29 \times (3 - 0)) - 7)}{(5 \times (8 + (6 \times (1 \times 4))))} &:= \frac{((2 - 93) \times (0 - 7))}{((5 + 86) \times 14)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (9 - (3 - (0 - 7))))}{(5 + (8 - (6 + (1^4))))} &:= \frac{(2 - (9 - (30 \times 7)))}{(58 \times (6 + (1^4)))} &:= \frac{(2 - (9 - (30 + 7)))}{(5 \times ((8 - (6 - 1)) \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (9 - (30 - 7)))}{((5 + (8 - (6 - 1))) \times 4)} &:= \frac{(2 - (9 \times (3 \times (0 \times 7))))}{(5 - (8 - (6 + (1^4))))} &:= \frac{(2 - (9 + (3 \times (0 - 7))))}{((5 + (8 - (6 \times 1))) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(586 + 14)}{(2 \times ((9 + 30) \times 7))} &:= \frac{(((5 \times 8) - (6 \times 1)) \times 4)}{(2 \times ((9 \times (3 - 0)) + 7))} &:= \frac{(5 \times (8 - (6 - 14)))}{(2 \times (9 - (3 \times (0 \times 7))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 + 8) \times (6 \times 14))}{(2 \times (9 - (3 \times (0 - 7))))} &:= \frac{(5 + (8 + (6 + (1 + 4))))}{(2 \times (9 - (3 + (0 - 7))))} &:= \frac{(((5 \times (8 - 6)) - 1) \times 4)}{(2 \times (9 \times (3 - (0 - 7))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times (8 \times (6 + (1 - 4))))}{(2 \times (9 + (3 - (0 \times 7))))} &:= \frac{(5 + ((8 \times 6) - (1^4)))}{(2 \times (9 + (3 - (0 - 7))))} &:= \frac{(5 \times (8 \times (6 - (1 - 4))))}{(2 \times (9 + (3 + (0 - 7))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + ((8 \times 6) - (1 + 4)))}{(2 \times (93 - (0 - 7)))} &:= \frac{((5 + (8 + (6 \times 1))) \times 4)}{(2 \times (93 + (0 - 7)))} &:= \frac{(5 + (8 + (6 + (1^4))))}{2^{9+3-07}} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times (8 \times (6 + (1 \times 4))))}{(2 + ((9 - (3 - 0)) \times 7))} &:= \frac{((58 \times (6 \times 1)) - 4)}{(2 + ((9 \times (3 - 0)) + 7))} &:= \frac{(58 + (6 \times (1^4)))}{(2 + ((9 \times (3 - 0)) - 7))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (86 + (1 - 4)))}{(2 + (9 - (3 - (0 \times 7))))} &:= \frac{((5 + (8 + (6 - 1))) \times 4)}{(2 + (9 - (3 - (0 - 7))))} &:= \frac{(((5 \times (8 - 6)) + 1) \times 4)}{(2 + (9 - (3 \times (0 \times 7))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 + (8 + (6 + (1 - 4))))}{(2 + (9 - (3 + (0 - 7))))} &:= \frac{(5 - (8 - (6 - (1^4))))}{(2 + (9 \times (3 - (0 \times 7))))} &:= \frac{(5 + (8 + (6 - (1 - 4))))}{(2 + (9 \times (3 - (0 - 7))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(5 \times (8 - (6 - (1 \times 4))))}{(2 + (9 + (3 - (0 - 7))))} &:= \frac{(5 + ((8 \times 6) + (1 + 4)))}{(2 + (9 + (3 + (0 - 7))))} &:= \frac{(((5 \times 8) + (6 \times 1)) \times 4)}{(2 + (9 + (30 + 7)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((5 - (8 - 6)) \times 14)}{(5 + (8 + (6 - (1 + 4))))} &:= \frac{(5 + (8 + (6 - (1 + 4))))}{(5 + (86 + (1 + 4)))} &:= \frac{(5 + (86 + (1 + 4)))}{(5 + (86 + (1 + 4)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(2 + (9 + (30 - 7)))}{(58 + (6 + (1 \times 4)))} := \frac{(2 + (93 - (0 \times 7)))}{(5 \times (8 + (6 \times (1 + 4))))} := \frac{(2 + (93 - (0 - 7)))}{((5 \times (8 \times (6 - 1))) + 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(29 - (3 \times (0 - 7)))}{5^{8-6 \times 1} \times 4} := \frac{(29 - (3 + (0 - 7)))}{((5 \times (8 + (6 \times 1))) - 4)} := \frac{(29 - (30 - 7))}{(5 + (8 - (6 - (1 + 4))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(29 \times (3 - (0 \times 7)))}{(58 \times (6 + (1 - 4)))} := \frac{(29 \times (3 - (0 - 7)))}{(58 \times (6 + (1 \times 4)))} := \frac{(29 + (3 - (0 - 7)))}{(5 + (8 + (61 + 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(29 + (3 + (0 - 7)))}{(5 \times (8 + (6 - (1 \times 4))))} := \frac{(29 + (30 + 7))}{(((5 \times 8) - (6 + 1)) \times 4)} := \frac{(29 + (30 - 7))}{(((5^{8-6}) + 1) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{29 + 307}{58 + 614} := \frac{293 - 0 \times 7}{586 \times (1^4)} := \frac{293 - 07)}{586 - 14}
 \end{aligned}$$

► **32058**
96174

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((3 \times (2 - 0))^5) \times 8)}{(9 \times ((6 - (1 - 7))^4))} := \frac{(((3^2 + 0) - 5) \times 8)}{(96 \times (1^{74}))} := \frac{(((3 + (2 - 0)) \times 5) + 8)}{(9 \times (6 + ((1^7) + 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 - (2 + (0 - 5))) \times 8)}{(9 \times (6 - (1 - (7 + 4))))} := \frac{((3 \times (2 - (0 - 5))) - 8)}{(9 + (6 \times ((1^7) + 4)))} := \frac{((3 \times (2 \times (0 + 5))) - 8)}{((9 \times (6 + 1)) + (7 - 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (2 - 0)) + 58)}{(9 + (61 \times (7 - 4)))} := \frac{((3 \times (20 + 5)) - 8)}{(9 + (6 \times ((1 + 7) \times 4)))} := \frac{((3 \times (20 - 5)) + 8)}{(((9 \times 6) - 1) \times (7 - 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times 20) + (5 - 8))}{(9 - (6 \times (1 - (7 \times 4))))} := \frac{3^2 + 0 \times 5 + 8}{((9 \times (6 \times 1)) - (7 - 4))} := \frac{((3^2 + 0) - (5 - 8))}{(9 \times (6 + (1 - (7 - 4))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3^2 + 0) \times (5 + 8))}{(9 \times (((6 - 1) \times 7) + 4))} := \frac{((3^2 + 0) \times 58)}{(9 \times (6 \times (1 + (7 \times 4))))} := \frac{((3 + (2 - (0 \times 5))) \times 8)}{(96 - ((1 - 7) \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 + (2 - (0 - 5))) \times 8)}{(((9 \times 6) - (1 - 7)) \times 4)} := \frac{((3 + (2 - 0)) \times (5 + 8))}{((9 + 6) \times (17 - 4))} := \frac{((3 + (20 - 5)) \times 8)}{(9 \times ((6 - (1 - 7)) \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 + 2)^{-05+8})}{(((9 \times 6) - 1) \times 7) + 4} := \frac{(3 - ((2 \times (0 - 5)) - 8))}{(9 \times (6 + (1^{74})))} := \frac{(3 - ((2 + (0 - 5)) \times 8))}{9^{6-1-7+4}} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (2 - (0 - (5 - 8))))}{(9 + (6 - (1 \times (7 - 4))))} := \frac{(3 - (2 - (0 \times 58)))}{(9 - (6 \times (1^{74})))} := \frac{(3 - (2 \times ((0 \times 5) - 8)))}{(9 + ((6 - (1 - 7)) \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (2 \times (0 - (5 + 8))))}{(9 + (6 \times (17 - 4)))} := \frac{(3 - (2 \times (0 \times 58)))}{9^{6-1^7-4}} := \frac{(3 - (2 + (0 - (5 \times 8))))}{(96 - (1 - (7 \times 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (2 + (0 - (5 + 8))))}{(9 + (6 - (1 - (7 \times 4))))} := \frac{(3 - (2 + (0 - 58)))}{(9 + (6 \times (1 \times (7 \times 4))))} := \frac{(3 - (20 - (5 \times 8)))}{(3 - (20 - (5 \times 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times ((2 - (0 - 5)) \times 8))}{(9 \times ((6 + (1 + 7)) \times 4))} := \frac{(3 \times ((2 - (0 - 5))^8))}{(9 \times (((6 + 1) \times 7)^4))} := \frac{(3 \times ((2 \times (0 + 5)) + 8))}{(9 \times (6 \times (1 \times (7 - 4))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times ((2^{05}) + 8))}{((96 + (1 - 7)) \times 4)} := \frac{(3 \times ((2^{05}) - 8))}{(9 \times (6 \times (1 + (7 - 4))))} := \frac{(3 \times ((20 \times 5) + 8))}{(961 + (7 + 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times ((20 \times 5) - 8))}{(9 \times ((6 + 17) \times 4))} := \frac{(3 \times (2 - ((0 \times 5) - 8)))}{(9 + (6 + (1 + 74)))} := \frac{(3 \times (2 - (0 - (5 + 8))))}{(9 + (6 \times (17 + 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (2 - (0 \times 58)))}{(9 \times (6 - (1 + (7 - 4))))} := \frac{(3 \times (2 \times (0 - (5 - 8))))}{(9 \times (6 \times (1^{74})))} := \frac{(3 \times (2 \times (0 + (5 \times 8))))}{(9 \times (6 + (1 \times 74)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (2^{-05+8}))}{(9 \times (6 - (1 - (7 - 4))))} := \frac{(3 \times (2 + (0 - (5 - 8))))}{(9 \times (6 - (1^{74})))} := \frac{(3 \times (20 \times (5 \times 8)))}{(96 \times (1 + 74))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (20 + (5 + 8)))}{(9 \times (6 - (1 - (7 \times 4))))} := \frac{(3 \times (20 + (5 - 8)))}{(3 \times (20 + (5 - 8)))} := \frac{(3 \times (20 + 58))}{(3 \times (20 + 58))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3^2 + 0 \times 58)}{(9 \times (6 - (1 \times (7 - 4))))} := \frac{3^{2-05+8}}{(9 \times (6 + (1 + 74)))} := \frac{3^{20-5-8}}{9^{6+1-7+4}} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + ((2^{05}) + 8))}{((9 \times 6) + (1 + 74))} := \frac{(3 + ((20 \times 5) - 8))}{((96 - 1) \times (7 - 4))} := \frac{(3 + (2 - (0 - (5 - 8))))}{(9 - (6 - (1 \times (7 - 4))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(3 + (2 - (0 \times 58)))}{(9 + (6 \times (1^{74})))} & := \frac{(3 + (2 - (0 - 58)))}{(9 + (6 + 174))} & := \frac{(3 + (2^{-05+8}))}{(9 + (6 \times (1 + (7 - 4))))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 + (2 + (0 - (5 - 8))))}{(9 - (6 - (17 + 4)))} & := \frac{(3 + (20 - (5 + 8)))}{(9 - (6 + (1 - (7 \times 4))))} & := \frac{(3 + (20 - (5 - 8)))}{(9 - (6 - (1 + 74)))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 + (20 + (5 + 8)))}{((9 + (6 + 1)) \times 7) - 4)} & := \frac{(3 + (20 + (5 - 8)))}{((9 + (6 \times (1^7))) \times 4)} & := \frac{(3 + (20 + 58))}{(9 \times (6 + (17 + 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 + (205 + 8))}{(9 \times (6 \times (1 + (7 + 4))))} & := \frac{(3 + 2058)}{(9 + 6174)} & := \frac{(32 - (0 - 58))}{(9 \times (6 \times ((1^7) + 4)))} \\
 & := \frac{(32 \times (0 - (5 - 8)))}{(96 \times (1 \times (7 - 4)))} & := \frac{(32 \times (0 + (5 + 8)))}{(96 \times (17 - 4))} & := \frac{(320 + 58)}{(9 \times (6 \times (17 + 4)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.66 70 Equivalent Blocks

► $\frac{15486}{30972}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{((1^5) + (4 \times 86))}{(30 \times (9 + (7 \times 2)))} & := \frac{((1 + (5 \times 4)) \times (8 - 6))}{(3 - (0 - (9 + 72)))} & := \frac{((1 + (5 + (4 + 8))) \times 6)}{(3 \times ((0 \times 9) + 72))} \\
 & := \frac{((1 + (5 + 4)) \times (8 \times 6))}{(30 \times ((9 + 7) \times 2))} & := \frac{((1 + (5 + 4))^{8-6})}{((3 - (0 - 97)) \times 2)} & := \frac{((1 + (5 - 4)) \times (8 + 6))}{((30 - (9 - 7)) \times 2)} \\
 & := \frac{((1 + 5) \times (4 \times (8 \times 6)))}{((3 \times (0 + (9 + 7)))^2)} & := \frac{((1 + 5)^{4-8+6})}{((3 \times (0 \times 9)) + 72)} & := \frac{((15 \times 4) - (8 + 6))}{((30 + (9 + 7)) \times 2)} \\
 & := \frac{((15 - 4) \times 86)}{((30 \times (9 \times 7)) + 2)} & := \frac{((154 + 8) \times 6)}{(3 \times (0 + (9 \times 72)))} & := \frac{(1 - ((5 - (4 + 8)) \times 6))}{(((3 - (0 - 9)) \times 7) + 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - ((5 \times (4 - 8)) - 6))}{(3 \times (0 + (9 + (7 + 2))))} & := \frac{(1 - (5 - ((4 \times 8) + 6)))}{(3 - (0 - ((9 \times 7) + 2)))} & := \frac{(1 - (5 - (4 + (8 \times 6))))}{(3 \times (0 + ((9 + 7) \times 2)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (5 - (4 + (8 - 6))))}{((3 \times (0 + (9 - 7))) - 2)} & := \frac{(1 - (5 - (48 - 6)))}{((3 \times (0 + 9)) + (7^2))} & := \frac{(1 - (5 \times (4 - (8 + 6))))}{(3 - (0 - (97 + 2)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (5 + ((4 - 8) \times 6)))}{(((3 \times (0 + 9)) - 7) \times 2)} & := \frac{(1 - (5 + (4 - (8 + 6))))}{(3 \times (0 + (9 - (7 - 2))))} & := \frac{(1 - (5 + (4 - 86)))}{(30 + (9 \times (7 \times 2)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 - (54 - 86))}{(3 + (0 - (9 - 72)))} & := \frac{(1 \times ((5 - (4 - 8)) \times 6))}{((3 - (0 - 9)) \times (7 + 2))} & := \frac{(1 \times ((5 \times (4 + 8)) + 6))}{((3 - (0 - (9 \times 7))) \times 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times ((5 + (4 \times 8)) \times 6))}{(3 - (0 - (9 \times (7^2))))} & := \frac{(1 \times ((5 + 4) \times (8 \times 6)))}{((3 - (0 - 9)) \times 72)} & := \frac{(1 \times ((5 + 4) \times (8 - 6)))}{((3 \times (0 + (9 - 7)))^2)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (5 - ((4 - 8) \times 6)))}{((30 \times (9 - 7)) - 2)} & := \frac{(1 \times (5 - (4 - (8 \times 6))))}{(3 - (0 - (97 - 2)))} & := \frac{(1 \times (5 - (4 - (8 + 6))))}{(30 - (9 - (7 + 2)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (5 - (4 - (8 - 6))))}{(3 \times ((0 \times 97) + 2))} & := \frac{(1 \times (5 - (4 - 86)))}{(3 \times (0 + (9 + (7^2))))} & := \frac{(1 \times (5 \times ((4 \times 8) - 6)))}{(309 - (7^2))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (5 \times (4 - (8 - 6))))}{((3 - ((0 \times 9) - 7)) \times 2)} & := \frac{(1 \times (5 \times (4 + (8 - 6))))}{((3 - (0 - 9)) \times (7 - 2))} & := \frac{(1 \times (5 \times (48 + 6)))}{(30 \times (9 + (7 + 2)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (5 \times (48 - 6)))}{(30 \times (9 + (7 - 2)))} & := \frac{(1 \times (5^{4-8+6}))}{((3 \times (0 + (9 + 7))) + 2)} & := \frac{(1 \times (5 + (4 - (8 - 6))))}{((3 \times (0 \times 9)) + (7 \times 2))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (5 + (4 \times (8 - 6))))}{(3 - (0 - (9 + (7 \times 2))))} & := \frac{(1 \times (5 + (4^{8-6})))}{(3 \times (0 + (9 + (7 - 2))))} & := \frac{(1 \times (5 + (4 + (8 + 6))))}{((3 \times (0 + (9 + 7))) - 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(1 \times (54 \times (8 + 6)))}{((30 - 9) \times 72)} & := \frac{1^{5486}}{((3 \times (0 \times 97)) + 2)} & := \frac{(1 + ((5 \times 4) + (8 + 6)))}{(30 - (9 - (7^2)))} \\
 & := \frac{(1 + ((5^4) - (8 \times 6)))}{(((3 \times (0 + 9)) + 7)^2)} & := \frac{(1 + ((5 + 4) \times (8 + 6)))}{((30 + 97) \times 2)} & := \frac{(1 + ((5 + 4) \times (8 - 6)))}{((3 - (0 - (9 + 7))) \times 2)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(1 + ((54 - 8) \times 6))}{(((30 \times 9) + 7) \times 2)} := \frac{(1 + (5 - (4 - (8 \times 6))))}{((3 - ((0 \times 9) - 7))^2)} := \frac{(1 + (5 - (4 - (8 + 6))))}{((3 \times (0 + 9)) + (7 - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (5 - (4 - (8 - 6))))}{(3 + (0 - (9 - (7 \times 2))))} := \frac{(1 + (5 \times (4 - (8 - 6))))}{((3 \times (0 - 9)) + (7^2))} := \frac{(1 + (5 \times (4 \times (8 - 6))))}{(((3 - (0 - 9)) \times 7) - 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (5 \times (4 + (8 - 6))))}{((30 \times (9 - 7)) + 2)} := \frac{(1 + (5 \times (4 + 86)))}{((30^{9-7}) + 2)} := \frac{(1 + (5^{4-8+6}))}{(3 - ((0 \times 9) - (7^2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (5 + ((4 \times 8) + 6)))}{(30 + (9 + (7^2)))} := \frac{(1 + (5 + ((4 \times 8) - 6)))}{(3 - (0 - ((9 \times 7) - 2)))} := \frac{(1 + (5 + (4 - (8 - 6))))}{(30 - (9 + (7 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (5 + (4 \times (8 - 6))))}{((30 - (9 + 7)) \times 2)} := \frac{(1 + (5 + (4^{8-6})))}{(30 + (9 + (7 - 2)))} := \frac{(1 + (5 + (4 + (8 + 6))))}{(3 - (0 - (9 \times (7 - 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(1 + (5 + (48 \times 6)))}{((3 - (0 - 9)) \times (7^2))} := \frac{(1 + (5 + (48 + 6)))}{(3 \times (0 - (9 - (7^2))))} := \frac{(15 - (4 + (8 - 6)))}{(3^{09-7} \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(15 + (4 - (8 + 6)))}{((3 - (0 - (9 - 7))) \times 2)} := \frac{(15 + (4 - (8 - 6)))}{(30 + (9 - (7 - 2)))} := \frac{(15 + 486)}{(30 + 972)} \\
 &:= \frac{(154 - (8 - 6))}{(309 - (7 - 2))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► **32079**
64158

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((3 \times (2 - 0)) + 7) \times 9)}{(6 - (4 \times (1 - 58)))} := \frac{(((3 - (2 + (0 - 7))) \times 9)}{(6 \times ((4 - (1^5)) \times 8))} := \frac{(((3 - (2 - 0)) \times (7 \times 9))}{(6 + ((4 - 1) \times (5 \times 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((3 - (2 - 0)) \times (7 + 9))}{((6 \times (4 \times (1^5))) + 8)} := \frac{(((3 - (2 - 0)) \times 79)}{(6 + ((4 + 15) \times 8))} := \frac{(((3 \times (2 - (0 - 7))) + 9)}{(6 \times (4 + ((1^5) \times 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((3 \times (2 - (0 - 7))) - 9)}{(6 \times (4 - (1 + (5 - 8))))} := \frac{(((3 \times (2 \times (0 + 7))) + 9)}{(6 \times (4 + (1 \times (5 + 8))))} := \frac{(((3 \times (2 \times (0 + 7))) - 9)}{(6 \times (4 + (15 - 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((3 \times (2 - 0)) + (7 + 9))}{(6 + (41 + (5 - 8)))} := \frac{(((3 \times (2 - 0)) + (7 - 9))}{(6 + (4 + (1 + (5 - 8))))} := \frac{(((3 \times (2 - 0)) + 79)}{(6 + (4 \times (1 + (5 \times 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((3 \times (20 + 7)) + 9)}{(6 + ((4 - 1) \times 58))} := \frac{(((3 \times (20 - 7)) - 9)}{(6 - (4 - (1 \times 58)))} := \frac{(((3 \times 20) - (7 + 9))}{((6 + (4 + (1^5))) \times 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((3 \times 20) + (7 + 9))}{((6 \times (4 \times (1 + 5))) + 8)} := \frac{(((3 \times 20) + (7 - 9))}{((6 - (4 \times 1)) \times 58)} := \frac{(((3^2 + 0) - (7 - 9))}{((3^2 + 0) - (7 - 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((3^2 + 0) + 79)}{((6 - (4 \times (1 - 5))) \times 8)} := \frac{(((3 + (2 - (0 \times 7))) \times 9)}{((6 + 4) \times ((1^5) + 8))} := \frac{(((3 + (2 - (0 \times 7)))^9)}{((6 + (4 \times 1)) \times (5^8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((3 + (2 - (0 - 7))) \times 9)}{6^{4-158}} := \frac{(((3 - 2) \times (0 - (7 - 9)))}{(6 - (4 + (1 + (5 - 8))))} := \frac{(((3 - 20) \times (7 - 9))}{(6 + (4 + (1 \times 58)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - ((2 \times (0 - 7)) + 9))}{(6 - (4 - (1 + (5 + 8))))} := \frac{(3 - ((2 \times (0 - 7)) - 9))}{((6 \times (4 + (1 + 5))) - 8)} := \frac{(3 - ((2 + (0 - 7)) \times 9))}{(6 \times (4 \times (1 - (5 - 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (2 - (0 \times 79)))}{(6 - (4 \times 1^{58}))} := \frac{(3 - (2 \times (0 - (7 \times 9))))}{(6 \times (4 - (1 - (5 \times 8))))} := \frac{(3 - (2 \times (0 - (7 + 9))))}{(6 + ((4 - (1 - 5)) \times 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (2 \times (0 \times 79)))}{(6 - (4 \times (1 - (5 - 8))))} := \frac{(3 - (2 + ((0 \times 7) - 9)))}{(((6 - 4) \times (1 + 5)) + 8)} := \frac{(3 - (2 + (0 - (7 \times 9))))}{(6 + ((4 + (1 + 5)) \times 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (2 + (0 - (7 + 9))))}{(6 + (4 \times (15 - 8)))} := \frac{(3 - (2 + (0 - 79)))}{(6 - (4 - 158))} := \frac{(3 - (20 \times (7 - 9)))}{(6 + ((4 + (1 + 5)) \times 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times ((2 \times (0 \times 7)) + 9))}{(6 - (4 \times (1 - (5 + 8))))} := \frac{(3 \times ((2 \times (0 + 7)) + 9))}{(6 \times (((4 - 1) \times 5) + 8))} := \frac{(3 \times ((2 \times (0 + 7)) - 9))}{(6 \times (4 + ((1^5)^8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (2 - (0 - (7 \times 9))))}{(6 \times ((4 + 1) \times (5 + 8)))} := \frac{(3 \times (2 - (0 - (7 + 9))))}{(6 \times (4 + (1 + (5 + 8))))} := \frac{(3 \times (2 - (0 \times 79)))}{(3 \times (2 - (0 \times 79)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (2 - (0 - 79)))}{(6 + (4 \times (15 \times 8)))} := \frac{(3 \times (2 \times (0 + (7 + 9))))}{(6 \times (4 \times ((1^5) \times 8)))} := \frac{(3 \times (2^{0 \times 7 + 9}))}{(64 \times ((1 + 5) \times 8))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(3 \times (2^{-07+9}))}{(6 + (4 + (1 + (5 + 8))))} := \frac{(3 \times (20 + 79))}{(6 \times (41 + 58))} := \frac{(3 \times (207 + 9))}{6^4 \times 1^{58}} \\
 & := \frac{3^{2 \times 0 \times 7 + 9}}{(6 \times ((4 - (1^5))^8))} := \frac{3^2 + 0 \times 79}{(6 - (4 \times (1 \times (5 - 8))))} := \frac{3^{2-07+9}}{(6 - (4 \times (1 - (5 \times 8))))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 + ((2^{07}) + 9))}{(((6 \times (4 + 1)) + 5) \times 8)} := \frac{(3 + ((20 \times 7) + 9))}{((6 \times 41) + 58)} := \frac{(3 + ((20 \times 7) - 9))}{((6 \times (41 + 5)) - 8)} \\
 & := \frac{(3 + ((20 - 7) \times 9))}{(6 \times ((4 + (1^5)) \times 8))} := \frac{(3 + (2 - ((0 \times 7) - 9)))}{(3 + (2 - ((0 \times 7) - 9)))} := \frac{(3 + (2 - (0 - (7 \times 9))))}{(3 + (2 - (0 - (7 \times 9))))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 + (2 - (0 - (7 + 9))))}{(6 \times (4 - (1 \times (5 - 8))))} := \frac{(3 + (2 - (0 \times 79)))}{(6 + (4 \times 1^{58}))} := \frac{(3 + (2 - (0 - 79)))}{(6 + (4 + 158))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 + (2^{-07+9}))}{(6 + (4 + (1 - (5 - 8))))} := \frac{(3 + (20 - (7 - 9)))}{(6 + (4 + (1 \times (5 \times 8))))} := \frac{(3 + (20 + (7 + 9)))}{(6 \times (4 + ((1^5) + 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 + 2079)}{(6 + 4158)} := \frac{(32 - ((0 \times 7) - 9))}{((6 \times (4 \times 1)) + 58)} := \frac{(32 - (0 \times 79))}{((6 - (4 - (1 + 5))) \times 8)} \\
 & := \frac{(320 - (7 - 9))}{(64 + 158)} := \frac{(32 \times ((0 \times 7) + 9))}{(64 \times ((1^5) + 8))} := \frac{(32 + ((0 \times 7) - 9))}{(6 + ((4 + (1^5)) \times 8))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► **48513**
97026

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(((4 + 8) \times 5) + 1) \times 3}{(((9 \times (7 - 0)) - 2) \times 6)} := \frac{(((4 \times (8 \times 5)) + 1) \times 3)}{(970 + (2 - 6))} := \frac{(((4 \times 8) - 5) \times 13)}{(9 \times (70 + (2 + 6)))} \\
 & := \frac{(((4 + 8) \times (5 + 1)) - 3)}{((9 - (7 \times (0 - 2))) \times 6)} := \frac{(((4 \times (8 \times (5 + 1))) + 3)}{(((9 \times (7 - 0)) + 2) \times 6)} := \frac{(((4 \times (8 \times (5 - 1))) + 3)}{(((9 + (7 - 0))^2) + 6)} \\
 & := \frac{(((9 - (7 \times (0 - 2))) \times 6)}{((4 \times (8 \times (5 - 1))) - 3)} := \frac{(((4 \times (85 + 1)) + 3)}{((9 \times 70) + (2^6))} := \frac{(((4 \times (85 - 1)) - 3)}{(9 \times (70 - (2 - 6)))} \\
 & := \frac{(((9 + (7 - 0))^2) - 6)}{((4 \times 8) - (5 + (1^3)))} := \frac{((4 \times 8) + (5 \times (1 + 3)))}{(9 \times ((70 \times 2) + 6))} := \frac{((4 \times 85) - 13)}{((9 \times (70 + 2)) + 6)} \\
 & := \frac{4^{8-5+1} \times 3}{(((9 + (7 - 0))^2) \times 6)} := \frac{((4 + ((8 \times 5) + 1)) \times 3)}{(9 \times ((7 + (0 - 2)) \times 6))} := \frac{((4 + (8 - (5 - 1)))^3)}{((9 + (7 - 0)) \times (2^6))} \\
 & := \frac{(((4 + (8 + (5 + 1))) \times 3)}{((9 + (7 - (0 - 2))) \times 6)} := \frac{((4 + (8 + 51)) \times 3)}{(9 \times (7 \times ((0 \times 2) + 6)))} := \frac{((4 + 8) \times (51 \times 3))}{((4 + 8) \times (51 \times 3))} \\
 & := \frac{((48 - (5 + 1)) \times 3)}{(9 \times (7 \times (0 - (2 - 6))))} := \frac{((48 \times (5 \times 1)) + 3)}{(9 \times ((7 - (0 - 2)) \times 6))} := \frac{((48 \times (5 + 1)) + 3)}{(97 \times ((0 \times 2) + 6))} \\
 & := \frac{((48 \times (5 + 1)) - 3)}{((97 + (0 - 2)) \times 6)} := \frac{((48 + 51) \times 3)}{(9 \times (70 + (2 - 6)))} := \frac{(4 - (8 - (5 - (1 - 3))))}{(9 - (7 - (0 - (2 - 6))))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 - (8 - (5 \times (1^3))))}{(9 - (7 - (0 \times 26)))} := \frac{(4 - (8 - (5 + (1^3))))}{(9 + (7 + (0 - (2 \times 6))))} := \frac{(4 - (8 - (5 + 13)))}{(9 - (7 + (0 - 26)))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 - (8 + (5 - 13)))}{(9 + (7 + (0 - (2 + 6))))} := \frac{(4 - (85 \times (1 - 3)))}{((9 + (7^{02})) \times 6)} := \frac{(4 \times ((8^5 \times 1)^3))}{(((9 + (7 - 0))^2)^6)} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times ((8 + 5) \times (1 + 3)))}{((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 26)} := \frac{(4 \times (8 - (5 \times (1^3))))}{(9 + (7 - (0 - (2 + 6))))} := \frac{(4 \times (8 - (5 - 13)))}{((9 - (7 - 0)) \times (2^6))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times (8 \times (5 - (1^3))))}{((9 - (7 - 0))^{2+6})} := \frac{(4 \times (8 \times (5 + (1 - 3))))}{((9 + (7 - 0)) \times (2 \times 6))} := \frac{4 \times 8^{5-1-3}}{(9 + ((7^{02}) + 6))} \\
 & := \frac{4 \times 8^{5-1+3}}{((9 + (7 - (0 \times 2)))^6)} := \frac{4 \times 8^{5+1+3}}{((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 2)^6} := \frac{4 \times 8^{5+1-3}}{((9 - (7 + (0 - 2)))^6)} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times (8 + (5 - (1 \times 3))))}{(9 + (7 - (0 - (2^6))))} := \frac{(4 \times (8 + (5 - (1^3))))}{((9 + (7 - (0 \times 2))) \times 6)} := \frac{(4 \times (8 + (5 - (1 - 3))))}{((9 \times (7 \times (0 + 2))) - 6)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (85 - (1 \times 3)))}{((9 \times 70) + 26)} &:= \frac{(4 + ((8 \times (5 - 1)) - 3))}{(9 - (7 + (0 - (2^6))))} &:= \frac{(4 + ((8 \times 5) + (1 - 3)))}{((9 + (7 + (0 - 2))) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + ((8^5) - (1 + 3)))}{(9 + 7)^{-02+6}} &:= \frac{(4 + (8 - (5 - (1 \times 3))))}{(9 + (7 + (0 - (2 - 6))))} &:= \frac{(4 + (8 - (5 - (1^3))))}{(9 + (7 - (0 \times 26)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 - (5 - (1 + 3))))}{(9 + (7 - ((0 \times 2) - 6)))} &:= \frac{(4 + (8 - (5 - (1 - 3))))}{(9 - (7 + (0 - (2 + 6))))} &:= \frac{(4 + (8 - (5 \times (1^3))))}{(9 - (7 + (0 - (2 \times 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 - (5 + (1^3))))}{(9 + (7 - (0 - (2 - 6))))} &:= \frac{(4 + (8 \times ((5 - 1) \times 3)))}{((97 \times (0 + 2)) + 6)} &:= \frac{(4 + (8 \times (5 - (1^3))))}{(9 \times ((7 \times (0 + 2)) - 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 \times (5 + (1 + 3))))}{(((9 + 70) \times 2) - 6)} &:= \frac{(4 + (8 \times (51 - 3)))}{(97 \times (0 + (2 + 6)))} &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + (5 - (1 + 3))))}{(((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 2) - 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + (5 - (1 - 3))))}{(((9 + (7 - 0)) \times 2) + 6)} &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + (5 \times (1 \times 3))))}{(9 \times ((7 \times (0 \times 2)) + 6))} &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + (5 + (1 + 3))))}{(9 + (7 - (0 - 26)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (8 + (51 + 3)))}{((9 \times (7 \times (0 + 2))) + 6)} &:= \frac{(4 + (85 + (1^3)))}{(9 \times ((7 \times (0 + 2)) + 6))} &:= \frac{(48 \times (5 + (1 + 3)))}{(9 \times (70 + 26))} \\
 &:= \frac{(485 - (1 + 3))}{(970 - (2 + 6))} &:= \frac{(485 - (1 - 3))}{(970 - (2 - 6))} &:= \frac{(485 + (1 + 3))}{(970 + (2 + 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{485 + 13}{970 + 26} &:= \frac{4851 + 3}{9702 + 6} &:= \frac{4851 - 3}{9702 - 6} \\
 &:= \frac{485 - 13}{970 - 26}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.67 71 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{23079}{46158} &:= \frac{(((2^3 + 0) \times 7) - 9)}{(46 + ((1 + 5) \times 8))} &:= \frac{(((2 + (3 - 0)) \times 7) - 9)}{(4 \times (6 + (15 - 8)))} &:= \frac{((2 - (3 \times (0 - 7))) \times 9)}{(46 \times ((1^5) + 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 - (3 + (0 - 7))) \times 9)}{((4 \times ((6 - 1) \times 5)) + 8)} &:= \frac{((2 \times (3 - (0 - 7))) + 9)}{(4 + (6 \times ((1^5) + 8)))} &:= \frac{((2 \times (3 \times (0 \times 7))) + 9)}{(4 + (6 + ((1^5) \times 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (3 \times (0 + 7))) + 9)}{(4 + ((6 \times 15) + 8))} &:= \frac{((2 \times (3 - 0)) + (7 + 9))}{(4 + ((6 - (1^5)) \times 8))} &:= \frac{((2 \times (3 - 0)) + (7 - 9))}{(4 \times (6 - (1 - (5 - 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (30 + 7)) + 9)}{(46 + (15 \times 8))} &:= \frac{((2 \times (30 + 7)) - 9)}{(4 + (6 + (15 \times 8)))} &:= \frac{((2 \times 3)^{-07+9})}{(4 \times (6 - (1 - (5 + 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times 30) - (7 + 9))}{(4 + (6 \times (1 + (5 + 8))))} &:= \frac{((2 \times 30) + (7 + 9))}{(4 \times (6 - ((1 - 5) \times 8)))} &:= \frac{((2 \times 30) + (7 - 9))}{(4 \times (6 + (15 + 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^{3+0 \times 7}) \times 9)}{((4 \times 6) + (15 \times 8))} &:= \frac{((2^{3+0 \times 7}) + 9)}{(46 + (1 - (5 + 8)))} &:= \frac{((2^3 + 0) \times (7 + 9))}{(4 \times (6 + (1 \times 58)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^3 + 0) + (7 \times 9))}{(4 + (6 \times (15 + 8)))} &:= \frac{((2 + (3 - (0 \times 7))) \times 9)}{((4 + 6) \times ((1^5) + 8))} &:= \frac{((2 + (3 - (0 \times 7)))^9)}{((4 + (6 \times 1)) \times (5^8))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 + (3 - (0 - 7))) \times 9)}{(4 \times (6 \times ((1^5) + 8)))} &:= \frac{((2 + (3 - 0)) \times (7 + 9))}{(4 \times ((6 - (1^5)) \times 8))} &:= \frac{((2 - 3) \times (0 - 79))}{(((4 + 6) \times 15) + 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - ((3 \times (0 - 7)) + 9))}{(4 + (6 \times (1 - (5 - 8))))} &:= \frac{(2 - (3 - (0 - (7 - 9))))}{(4 - (6 - (1 - (5 - 8))))} &:= \frac{(2 - (3 \times (0 - (7 + 9))))}{(4 + ((6 + (1 + 5)) \times 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (3 \times (0 \times 79)))}{(4 - ((6 - (1 + 5)) \times 8))} &:= \frac{(2 - (3 + (0 - (7 + 9))))}{(4 - (6 + ((1 - 5) \times 8)))} &:= \frac{(2 - (3 + (0 - 79)))}{(4 - (6 - 158))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (30 - (7 \times 9)))}{((4 + 6) \times (15 - 8))} &:= \frac{(2 \times ((3 - (0 - 7)) \times 9))}{((4 + (6 - 1)) \times (5 \times 8))} &:= \frac{(2 \times ((3 \times (0 + 7)) + 9))}{((4 + (6 + (1 \times 5))) \times 8)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((3 \times (0 + 7)) - 9))}{((4 \times (6 - (1 - 5))) + 8)} := \frac{(2 \times (3 - (0 - (7 \times 9))))}{(((4 \times (6 + 1)) + 5) \times 8)} := \frac{(2 \times (3 - (0 - (7 + 9))))}{(4 - (6 \times (1 - (5 + 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (3 - (0 \times 79)))}{(4 + (6 - (1 + (5 - 8))))} := \frac{(2 \times (3 - (0 - 79)))}{(4 \times ((6 \times 15) - 8))} := \frac{(2 \times (3 \times (0 - (7 - 9))))}{(4 + (6 + (1 + (5 + 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (3 \times (0 + (7 + 9))))}{(4 \times (6 \times ((1^5) \times 8)))} := \frac{(2 \times (3^{-07+9}))}{(4 \times (6 - (1 \times (5 - 8))))} := \frac{(2 \times (3 + (0 - (7 - 9))))}{(4 \times (6 - ((1^5)^8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (30 - (7 + 9)))}{(4 - (6 - (1 \times 58)))} := \frac{(2 \times (30 + (7 - 9)))}{(((4 + (6 - (1 - 5))) \times 8)} := \frac{2^3 + 0 \times 79}{4^{6-1+5-8}} \\
 &:= \frac{2^{3 \times (-07+9)}}{((4^{6+1-5}) \times 8)} := \frac{2^{3^{-07+9}}}{4^{6-1^{58}}} := \frac{2^{3-07+9}}{4^{6+1 \times 5-8}} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + ((3 - (0 - 7)) \times 9))}{(4 \times (6 + (1 \times (5 \times 8))))} := \frac{(2 + (3 - (0 - (7 \times 9))))}{(((4 \times (6 \times (1 + 5))) - 8)} := \frac{(2 + (3 - (0 - (7 + 9))))}{(4 + (6 - ((1 - 5) \times 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (3 - (0 - (7 - 9))))}{(4 + (6 - (1 - (5 - 8))))} := \frac{(2 + (3 - (0 \times 79)))}{(4 - (6 + (1 - (5 + 8))))} := \frac{(2 + (3 - (0 - 79)))}{(4 + (6 + 158))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (3^{-07+9}))}{(4 - (6 \times (1 \times (5 - 8))))} := \frac{(2 + (3 + (0 - (7 - 9))))}{(4 + (6 + (1 - (5 - 8))))} := \frac{(2 + (30 - (7 + 9)))}{(4 \times (6 - (1 + (5 - 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (30 - (7 - 9)))}{(4 + (6 + (1 \times 58)))} := \frac{(2 + (30 + (7 + 9)))}{(4 \times (6 \times (1 - (5 - 8))))} := \frac{(2 + (30 + (7 - 9)))}{(4 \times (6 + ((1^5) + 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (30 + 79))}{((46 \times (1 \times 5)) - 8)} := \frac{(2 + 3079)}{(4 + 6158)} := \frac{(23 - (0 - (7 \times 9)))}{(4 + ((6 + 15) \times 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(23 - (0 - (7 + 9)))}{(4 + (61 + (5 + 8)))} := \frac{(23 - (0 \times 79))}{(4 + (6 \times (15 - 8)))} := \frac{(23 - (0 - 79))}{((4 \times 61) - (5 \times 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(23 \times (0 - (7 - 9)))}{((4 \times (6 + 15)) + 8)} := \frac{(23^{-07+9})}{(46 \times (15 + 8))} := \frac{(23 + (0 - (7 - 9)))}{(4 + (6 + (1 \times (5 \times 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(230 - (7 - 9))}{(461 - (5 - 8))} := \frac{230 - 79}{4 \times 61 + 58}
 \end{aligned}$$

▶ **35481**
70962

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((3 \times 5) - 4) \times 8) + 1}{(70 + (9 \times (6 \times 2)))} := \frac{(((3 - (5 - 4)) \times 8) + 1)}{(7 + (0 - (9 - (6^2))))} := \frac{(((3 + 5)^4) \times (8 \times 1))}{((7 - (0 - 9))^{6-2})} \\
 &:= \frac{(((3 + 54) \times 8) - 1)}{(70 \times (9 + (6 - 2)))} := \frac{(((3 - 5) \times 4) + 81)}{((70 + (9 - 6)) \times 2)} := \frac{(((35 + 4) \times 8) + 1)}{((70 \times 9) - (6 - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((35 + 4) \times 8) - 1)}{((70 \times 9) - (6 + 2))} := \frac{((3 - (5 - 4)) \times (8 \times 1))}{((70 - (9 \times 6)) \times 2)} := \frac{((3 - (5 - 4)) \times (8 - 1))}{(7 - (0 - (9 + (6 \times 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 - (5 - 4))^{8-1})}{((70 - (9 \times 6))^2)} := \frac{((3 \times ((5 + 4) \times 8)) + 1)}{(7 \times ((0 \times 9) + 62))} := \frac{((3 \times (5 \times 4)) - (8 - 1))}{(70 + (9 \times (6 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (5 \times 4)) + (8 + 1))}{(((7 \times (0 + 9)) + 6) \times 2)} := \frac{((3 \times (5 \times 4)) + (8 - 1))}{((70 - (9 - 6)) \times 2)} := \frac{((3 \times (5 + (4 + 8))) - 1)}{((7 - (0 - (9 - 6)))^2)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (5 + 4)) + (8 \times 1))}{70^{9-6-2}} := \frac{((3 \times (5 + 48)) - 1)}{((70 + 9) \times (6 - 2))} := \frac{((3 \times 5) + 481)}{((7 - (0 - 9)) \times 62)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3^5) - ((4 \times 8) + 1))}{(70 \times ((9 - 6) \times 2))} := \frac{((3^5) - (48 - 1))}{(7 \times (0 + ((9 \times 6) + 2)))} := \frac{((3^5) + (4 - 81))}{((70 + 96) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 + (5 \times 4)) \times (8 \times 1))}{(((70 - 9) \times 6) + 2)} := \frac{((3 + (5 + 4)) \times (8 \times 1))}{((7 - (0 - 9)) \times (6 \times 2))} := \frac{((3 + (5 - 4)) \times (8 \times 1))}{((7 - (0 - 9)) \times (6 - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 + 5) \times (4 \times (8 + 1)))}{((7 - (0 - 9)) \times (6^2))} := \frac{((3 - 5) \times (4 - (8 \times 1)))}{(7 - (0 - ((9 - 6)^2)))} := \frac{((35 \times 4) - (8 + 1))}{(70 + (96 \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - ((5 \times (4 - 8)) + 1))}{((7 - (0 - (9 + 6))) \times 2)} := \frac{(3 - (5 - ((4 \times 8) + 1)))}{((7 \times (0 \times 9)) + 62)} := \frac{(3 - (5 - (4 \times (8 \times 1))))}{(7 + (0 - (9 - 62)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(3 - (5 - (4 \times (8 - 1))))}{(7 - (0 - (9 + (6^2))))} := \frac{(3 - (5 - (4 + (8 \times 1))))}{(7 - (0 - (9 + (6 - 2))))} := \frac{(3 - (5 - (48 + 1)))}{(((7 - (0 - 9)) \times 6) - 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (5 \times (4 - (8 + 1))))}{(7 \times ((0 \times 9) + (6 + 2)))} := \frac{(3 - (5 \times (4 - (8 - 1))))}{((7 \times (0 \times 9)) + (6^2))} := \frac{(3 - (5 + (4 - (8 \times 1))))}{(7 - (0 - (9 - (6 \times 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (5 + (4 - (8 - 1))))}{(7 + (0 - (9 - (6 - 2))))} := \frac{(3 \times (5 \times (48 + 1)))}{(70 \times (9 + (6 \times 2)))} := \frac{(3 \times (5 + (4 - (8 - 1))))}{(7 - (0 - (9 - (6 - 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (54 \times (8 - 1)))}{(7 \times (0 + (9 \times (6^2))))} := \frac{3^{5+4-8 \times 1}}{(7 + (0 - (9 - (6 + 2))))} := \frac{3^{5+4-8+1}}{(70 - ((9 \times 6) - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + ((5 \times (4 + 8)) + 1))}{((7 - (0 - 9)) \times (6 + 2))} := \frac{(3 + ((5 \times 4) + 81))}{((70 \times (9 - 6)) - 2)} := \frac{(3 + ((5 \times 48) + 1))}{((70 - 9) \times (6 + 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + ((5 \times 48) - 1))}{(((7 - (0 - (9 + 6)))^2)} := \frac{(3 + ((5^4) + (8 \times 1)))}{(((70 \times 9) + 6) \times 2)} := \frac{(3 + ((5 - 4) \times 81))}{(70 + (96 + 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (5 - (4 - (8 \times 1))))}{(7 - (0 - (9 + (6 + 2))))} := \frac{(3 + (5 - (4 - (8 + 1))))}{((7 - ((0 \times 9) - 6)) \times 2)} := \frac{(3 + (5 - (4 - 81)))}{((70 + (9 + 6)) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (5 \times (4 + (8 \times 1))))}{(70 + ((9 \times 6) + 2))} := \frac{(3 + (5 \times (48 - 1)))}{(((70 + 9) \times 6) + 2)} := \frac{(3 + (5 + ((4 \times 8) - 1)))}{(7 - (0 - (9 + 62)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (5 + (4 - (8 \times 1))))}{(7 - (0 - (9 - (6 + 2))))} := \frac{(3 + (5 + (4 - (8 - 1))))}{(7 + (0 - (9 - (6 \times 2))))} := \frac{(3 + (5 + (4 + (8 \times 1))))}{((7 \times ((0 \times 9) + 6)) - 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (5 + (4 + (8 + 1))))}{(7 \times (0 + ((9 - 6) \times 2))} := \frac{(3 + (5 + (48 + 1)))}{(((7 \times (0 + 9)) - 6) \times 2)} := \frac{(3 + (5 + (48 - 1)))}{((70 - (9 + 6)) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (54 - (8 \times 1)))}{(((7 - (0 - 9)) \times 6) + 2)} := \frac{(35 - (4 - (8 - 1)))}{(70 + ((9 - 6) \times 2))} := \frac{(35 - (4 \times (8 - 1)))}{(7 \times ((0 \times 96) + 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(35 \times (4 \times (8 + 1)))}{(70 \times (9 \times (6 - 2)))} := \frac{(35 \times (4 \times 81))}{(70 \times (9 \times (6^2)))} := \frac{(35 + (4 \times (8 + 1)))}{(70 + (9 \times (6 + 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(35 + (48 - 1))}{(70 + (96 - 2))} := \frac{35 + 481}{70 + 962} := \frac{354 - 8 \times 1}{70 \times 9 + 62} \\
 &:= \frac{3548 + 1}{7096 + 2} := \frac{3548 - 1}{7096 - 2}
 \end{aligned}$$

► **45186**
90372

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((4 + (5 \times 1)) \times 8) + 6)}{(9 - (0 - (3 \times (7^2))))} := \frac{(((4 + (5 \times 1)) \times 8) - 6)}{(90 + (3 \times (7 \times 2)))} := \frac{(((45 + 1) \times 8) - 6)}{((9^{03}) - (7 - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((4 - (5 \times (1 - 8))) \times 6)}{(9 \times (0 + (3 + (7^2))))} := \frac{(((4 - (5 + (1 - 8))) \times 6)}{(9 \times (0 + (3 + (7 - 2))))} := \frac{(((4 \times (5 - (1 - 8))) - 6)}{(9 - (0 - (3 + 72)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((4 \times (5 + (1^8))) + 6)}{((9 - (0 - (3 \times 7))) \times 2)} := \frac{(((4 \times (5 + (1^8))) - 6)}{(9 - (0 - (3 \times (7 + 2))))} := \frac{(((4 \times 5) - (1 + (8 - 6)))}{((9 \times (0 - (3 - 7))) - 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((4 \times 5) + (1 + (8 + 6)))}{(90 - ((3 + 7) \times 2))} := \frac{(((4 \times 5) + (18 \times 6))}{((9 - ((0 \times 3) - 7))^2)} := \frac{(((4 + (5 \times (1 + 8))) \times 6)}{((9 - (0 - 3)) \times (7^2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((4 + (5 \times 1)) \times (8 \times 6))}{((9 - (0 - 3)) \times 72)} := \frac{(((4 + (5 \times 1)) \times (8 + 6))}{(9 - (0 - (3^{7-2})))} := \frac{(((4 + (5 \times (1^8))) \times 6)}{(9 \times (0 + (3 + (7 + 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 + 5) \times (1 + (8 - 6)))}{(9 \times (0 - (3 - (7 + 2))))} := \frac{((4 + 5) \times (18 \times 6))}{(9 \times (0 + (3 \times 72)))} := \frac{((4 + 5) \times 186)}{(9 \times (0 + 372))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + 5)^{1^8+6}}{9^{0 \times 3+7} \times 2} := \frac{((4 + 518) \times 6)}{((90 - 3) \times 72)} := \frac{((45 + (1 + 8)) \times 6)}{(9 \times ((0 \times 3) + 72))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - ((5 - 18) \times 6))}{(90 + (37 \times 2))} := \frac{(4 - (5 - ((1^8) \times 6)))}{((9 - (0 - (3 - 7))) \times 2)} := \frac{(4 - (5 - ((1 + 8) \times 6)))}{((90 - 37) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (5 - (1 \times (8 + 6))))}{(9 - (0 - (3 + (7 \times 2))))} := \frac{(4 - (5 - (1 \times (8 - 6))))}{((9 \times (0 \times 37)) + 2)} := \frac{(4 - (5 - (1 + (8 \times 6))))}{(90 - (3 - (7 + 2)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(4 - (5 - (1 + (8 - 6))))}{(9 + ((0 \times 3) - (7 - 2)))} := \frac{(4 - (5 - (1 + 86)))}{((90 + (3 - 7)) \times 2)} := \frac{(4 - (5 \times (1 - (8 + 6))))}{((90 - (3 \times 7)) \times 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(4 - (5 + ((1 - 8) \times 6)))}{(((9 - (0 - 3)) \times 7) - 2)} := \frac{(4 - (5 + (1 - (8 \times 6))))}{((9 - (0 - 37)) \times 2)} := \frac{(4 - (5 + (1 - 86)))}{((9 - (0 - 3)) \times (7 \times 2))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times (5 - (1 - (8 + 6))))}{(9 \times ((0 - (3 - 7))^2))} := \frac{(4 \times (5 - (1^{86})))}{(9 - (0 - ((3 \times 7) + 2)))} := \frac{(4 \times (5 - (1 - 86)))}{((9^{03}) - (7 + 2))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times (5 \times (1 \times (8 - 6))))}{((90 + (3 + 7)) \times 2)} := \frac{(4 \times (5 \times (1^{86})))}{(((9 + (0 - 3)) \times 7) - 2)} := \frac{(4 \times (5 + ((1^8) \times 6)))}{((9 \times (0 + (3 + 7))) - 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(4 \times (5 + (1^{86})))}{(9 - (0 - (37 + 2)))} := \frac{(4 \times (5 + (1 + (8 \times 6))))}{((9 + (0 - 3)) \times 72)} := \frac{(4 \times (5 + (1 + (8 + 6))))}{((90 - (3 + 7)) \times 2)} \\
 & := \frac{(90 - (3 - (7^2)))}{(4 \times (5 + (18 - 6)))} := \frac{(4 + ((5 \times (1 \times 8)) - 6))}{((9 \times (0 + 3)) + (7^2))} := \frac{(90 + ((3 + 7) \times 2))}{(4 + ((5 \times (1 + 8)) + 6))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + ((5 \times (1 + 8)) - 6))}{(((9 - (0 - 3)) \times 7) + 2)} := \frac{(4 + ((5 + 18) \times 6))}{((90 \times 3) + (7 \times 2))} := \frac{(90 + ((3 + 7) \times 2))}{(4 + (5 - ((1 - 8) \times 6)))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + (5 - (1 - (8 + 6))))}{(9 - (0 - (37 - 2)))} := \frac{(4 + (5 - (1 \times (8 - 6))))}{(9 - ((0 \times 3) - (7 - 2)))} := \frac{(4 + (5 - (1^{86})))}{(90 - (37 \times 2))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + (5 - (1 - 86)))}{((90 - (3 - 7)) \times 2)} := \frac{(4 + (5 \times ((1^8) \times 6)))}{(((9 \times (0 + 3)) + 7) \times 2)} := \frac{(4 + (5 \times ((1^8) + 6)))}{(9 + (0 - (3 - 72)))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + (5 \times (1 \times (8 - 6))))}{(9 - (0 - ((3 \times 7) - 2)))} := \frac{(4 + (5 \times (1 + (8 - 6))))}{((9 \times (0 - (3 - 7))) + 2)} := \frac{(4 + (5 \times (1 \times (8 - 6))))}{(9 - ((0 \times 3) - (7^2)))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + (5 \times (1^{86})))}{(9 \times (0 - (3 - (7 - 2))))} := \frac{(4 + (5 + ((1^8) \times 6)))}{((9 + (0 - 3)) \times (7 - 2))} := \frac{(4 + (5 + ((1 + 8) \times 6)))}{(9 \times ((0 \times 3) + (7 \times 2)))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + (5 + (1 \times (8 - 6))))}{((9 \times (0 - 3)) + (7^2))} := \frac{(4 + (5 + (1 \times 86)))}{(90 + ((3 + 7)^2))} := \frac{(4 + (5 + (1^{86})))}{(9 + (0 - (3 - (7 \times 2))))} \\
 & := \frac{(4 + (5 + (1 + (8 - 6))))}{(9 - (0 - (3 \times (7 - 2))))} := \frac{(45 \times (1 \times (8 - 6)))}{(9 \times (0 + ((3 + 7) \times 2)))} := \frac{(45 \times (1 + (8 + 6)))}{(90 \times (3 \times (7 - 2)))} \\
 & := \frac{(45 \times (18 - 6))}{(90 \times (3 + (7 + 2)))} := \frac{(45 + ((1 + 8) \times 6))}{((90 \times 3) - 72)} := \frac{(45 + (18 \times 6))}{(90 + (3 \times 72))} \\
 & := \frac{(45 + 186)}{(90 + 372)} := \frac{(451 - (8 - 6))}{((90 \times (3 + 7)) - 2)}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.68 74 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30729}{61458} & := \frac{(((3 - (0 - 7)) \times 2) + 9)}{(6 + (1 \times (4 \times (5 + 8))))} := \frac{(((3 - (0 - 7)) \times 2) - 9)}{(6 - (1 - (4 + (5 + 8))))} := \frac{(((3 - (0 - 7))^2) \times 9)}{((6 - 1) \times (45 \times 8))} \\
 & := \frac{(((3 + (0 - 7)) \times 2) + 9)}{((6 \times (1 \times (4 - 5))) + 8)} := \frac{(((30 + 7) \times 2) + 9)}{(6 + (1 \times (4 \times (5 \times 8))))} := \frac{(((30 + 7) \times 2) - 9)}{((6 + (1 \times 4)) \times (5 + 8))} \\
 & := \frac{((3 - ((0 \times 7) - 2))^9)}{((6 + (1 \times 4)) \times (5^8))} := \frac{((3 - (0 - 7)) \times (2 \times 9))}{((6 - (1 - 4)) \times (5 \times 8))} := \frac{((3 - (0 - 7)) \times (2 + 9))}{((6 - 1) \times (4 + (5 \times 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{((3 - (0 - 7)) \times 29)}{((6 + (1 \times 4)) \times 58)} := \frac{((3 \times (0 \times 72)) + 9)}{(6 - (1 \times (4 \times (5 - 8))))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 + (7 \times 2))) + 9)}{(6 \times (1 \times (4 + (5 + 8))))} \\
 & := \frac{((3 \times (0 + (7^2))) + 9)}{(6 \times (1 \times (4 \times (5 + 8))))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 + (7 + 2))) + 9)}{(6 \times (1 \times ((4 \times 5) - 8)))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 + (7 + 2))) - 9)}{(6 \times (1 + (4 + (5 - 8))))} \\
 & := \frac{((3 \times (0 + (7 - 2))) + 9)}{(6 \times (1 + (4 - (5 - 8))))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 + (7 - 2))) - 9)}{(6 - (1 - (4 - (5 - 8))))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 + 7)) - (2 + 9))}{((6 \times (1 - (4 - 5))) + 8)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{((3 \times (0 + 7)) + (2 + 9))}{((6 + (1 - (4 - 5))) \times 8)} := \frac{3^{07-2} + 9}{((6 + 1) \times ((4 + 5) \times 8))} := \frac{3^{07-2} - 9}{(6 \times ((14 \times 5) + 8))} \\
 & := \frac{((30 - (7 \times 2)) \times 9)}{((6 \times (1 - (4 - 5))) \times 8)} := \frac{((30 \times (7 \times 2)) - 9)}{(6 \times (145 - 8))} := \frac{((30 \times (7 + 2)) - 9)}{((6 - (1 - 4)) \times 58)} \\
 & := \frac{((30 \times (7 - 2)) + 9)}{((6 \times (1 + (4 \times (5 + 8))))} := \frac{((30 \times 7) - (2 - 9))}{((6 + 1) \times (4 + 58))} := \frac{((30 \times 7) + (2 - 9))}{((6 + (1^4)) \times 58)} \\
 & := \frac{(3 - (0 - ((7 \times 2) + 9)))}{((6 \times (1 + (4 + 5))) - 8)} := \frac{(3 - (0 - ((7 \times 2) - 9)))}{(6 + (1 - (4 - (5 + 8))))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - ((7^2) + 9)))}{((6 \times (14 + 5)) + 8)} \\
 & := \frac{(3 - (0 - ((7^2) - 9)))}{(6 + ((1 + (4 + 5)) \times 8))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - ((7 - 2) \times 9)))}{(6 + (1 - (4 - (5 + 8))))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (7 - (2 - 9))))}{(6 + (1 \times ((4 \times 5) + 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 - (0 - (7 \times 29)))}{((6 \times (14 \times 5)) - 8)} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (7 + (2 \times 9))))}{((6 - (1 \times (4 - 5))) \times 8)} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (7 + (2 + 9))))}{(6 \times (1 \times (4 - (5 - 8))))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 - (0 - (7 + 29)))}{(6 \times (1 - (4 \times (5 - 8))))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (72 + 9)))}{(6 \times (1 \times ((4 \times 5) + 8)))} := \frac{6 \times 1^{458}}{(3 \times ((0 \times 72) + 9))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 + 1458)}{(3 \times (0 - (7 - (2 \times 9))))} := \frac{(6 \times (1 + ((4 \times 5) + 8)))}{(3 \times (0 - (7 - (2 + 9))))} := \frac{(6 \times (1 - ((4 - 5) \times 8)))}{(3 \times (0 - (7 - 29)))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 \times (14 + (5 - 8)))}{(3 \times (0 + ((7^2) + 9)))} := \frac{(6 + (1 + (4 + (5 + 8))))}{(3 \times (0 + ((7^2) - 9)))} := \frac{(((6 + 1) \times (4 \times 5)) - 8)}{(3 \times (0 + ((7 - 2) \times 9)))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 \times ((1^4) \times 58))}{(3 \times (0 + ((7 - 2)^9)))} := \frac{(6 \times ((1^4) \times (5 \times 8)))}{(3 \times (0 + (7 - (2 - 9))))} := \frac{(6 \times (1 + (4 + (5 \times 8))))}{(3 \times (0 + (7 + (2 + 9))))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 \times ((1 + 4) \times (5^8)))}{(3 \times (0 + (7 + 29)))} := \frac{(6 + ((14 \times 5) + 8))}{(3 \times (0 + (72 - 9)))} := \frac{(6 \times (1 + (4 + (5 + 8))))}{3^{-07+2+9}} \\
 & := \frac{((6 + (1 + (4 \times 5))) \times 8)}{(3 + (0 - (7 - (2 \times 9))))} := \frac{(6 \times (1 + (4 + 58)))}{(3 + (0 - (7 - (2 + 9))))} := \frac{(6 \times (14 + (5 + 8)))}{(3 + (0 - (7 - 29)))} \\
 & := \frac{((6 \times (1 - (4 - 5))) - 8)}{(30 - (7 - (2 \times 9)))} := \frac{(6 + (1 + (4 - (5 - 8))))}{(30 - (7 - (2 + 9)))} := \frac{(6 + (1 \times (4 + (5 \times 8))))}{(30 - (7 - (2 - 9)))} \\
 & := \frac{((6 \times (1 \times 4)) + 58)}{(30 - (7 \times (2 - 9)))} := \frac{(6 + (1 \times (4 + 58)))}{(30 - (7 + (2 \times 9)))} := \frac{(((6 - (1 - (4 - 5))) \times 8))}{(30 - (7 + (2 - 9)))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 - ((1 - (4 \times 5)) \times 8))}{(30 \times (7 + 29))} := \frac{(6 + ((1^4) - (5 - 8)))}{(30 + ((7 \times 2) + 9))} := \frac{(6 - (1 \times (4 - 58)))}{(30 + ((7 \times 2) - 9))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 \times (1 \times (45 \times 8)))}{(30 + ((7^2) - 9))} := \frac{((6 \times (14 + 5)) - 8)}{((6 \times (14 + 5)) - 8)} := \frac{(6 - ((1 - (4 + 5)) \times 8))}{(30 + (7 - (2 - 9)))} \\
 & := \frac{((6 - 1) \times ((4 \times 5) + 8))}{(30 + (72 + 9))} := \frac{(6 - (((1^4) - 5) \times 8))}{(30 + (72 - 9))} := \frac{((6 + ((1^4) \times 5)) \times 8)}{(307 - (2 - 9))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 \times (1 - (4 - (5 \times 8))))}{307 + 29} := \frac{((61 \times 4) - 58)}{307 - 29} := \frac{(((6 - 1)^4) - (5 - 8))}{614 + 58} \\
 & := \frac{307 + 29}{614 + 58} := \frac{307 - 29}{614 - 58}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.69 75 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20583}{61749} & := \frac{(((2 - (0 - 5)) \times 8) + 3)}{((6 \times (1 \times (7 \times 4))) + 9)} := \frac{(((2 - (0 - 5)) \times 8) - 3)}{((6 \times (1 \times (7 \times 4))) - 9)} := \frac{(((2 - (0 - 5))^8) \times 3)}{(((6 + 1) \times 7^4) \times 9)} \\
 & := \frac{(((2^{05}) - 8) \times 3)}{(6 \times (1 + (7 + (4 - 9))))} := \frac{(((20 \times 5) - 8) \times 3)}{((6 + 17) \times (4 \times 9))} := \frac{(((20 - 5) \times 8) - 3)}{(((6 - 1) \times 7) + 4) \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((2 - ((0 \times 5) - 8)) \times 3)}{(6 + (1 + (74 + 9)))} := \frac{((2 - (0 - (5 \times 8))) \times 3)}{((61 \times 7) - 49)} := \frac{((2 - (0 - (5 + 8))) \times 3)}{((6 \times (17 + 4)) + 9)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 - (0 - 5)) \times (8 \times 3))}{(6 \times (1 + (74 + 9)))} := \frac{((2 - (0 - 5)) \times (8 - 3))}{(6 + (1 \times ((7 + 4) \times 9)))} := \frac{((2 \times ((0 \times 5) + 8)) + 3)}{((6 \times (1 \times (7 + 4))) - 9)} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (0 - (5 - 8)))^3)}{(6 \times ((1 + (7 + 4)) \times 9))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 - (5 - 8))) + 3)}{(6 + (1 + (7 + (4 + 9))))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 \times 58)) + 3)}{(6 + (1 + (7 + (4 - 9))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (0 + (5 \times 8))) + 3)}{(6 - ((1 - (7 \times 4)) \times 9))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + (5 + 8))) - 3)}{((6 \times (17 - 4)) - 9)} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + 5)) + (8^3))}{(6 \times ((1 + (7 \times 4)) \times 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2 \times (0 + 5)) + 83)}{(((6 - 1) \times 7) - 4) \times 9)} := \frac{((2 \times (0 - 5)) + (8 \times 3))}{((6 + (1 - (7 \times (4 - 9))))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 - 5)) + (8 + 3))}{(6 - (1 + (7 + (4 - 9))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((2^{-05+8}) \times 3)}{(6 \times (1 \times (7 - (4 - 9))))} := \frac{((2^{05}) + (8 \times 3))}{(6 \times (1 + ((7 - 4) \times 9)))} := \frac{((2 + (0 - (5 - 8))) \times 3)}{((6 - (1^{74})) \times 9)} \\
 &:= \frac{((20 - (5 - 8)) \times 3)}{((6 \times (1 \times (7 - 4))) - 9)} := \frac{((20 \times 5) - (8 \times 3))}{(6 \times (1 + ((7 \times 4) + 9)))} := \frac{((20 \times 5) - (8 + 3))}{(6 + ((1 + (7 \times 4)) \times 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{((20 \times 5) + (8 - 3))}{((6 + (1 + (7 \times 4))) \times 9)} := \frac{((20 \times 5) - 83)}{((6 + ((1^7) + 4) \times 9))} := \frac{((20 + (5 + 8)) \times 3)}{((6 - (1 - (7 \times 4))) \times 9)} \\
 &:= \frac{((20 + (5 - 8)) \times 3)}{((6 + (1 \times (7 + 4))) \times 9)} := \frac{((20 + 58) \times 3)}{((6 \times ((17 - 4) \times 9))} := \frac{((20 - 5) \times (8 + 3))}{((6 - 1) \times ((7 + 4) \times 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 + (1 \times (7 + 4))) \times 9)}{(2 - ((0 \times 5) - (8 \times 3)))} := \frac{(2 - ((0 \times 5) - (8 + 3)))}{((6 \times ((1^7) + 4) \times 9))} := \frac{(2 - ((0 \times 5) - (8 - 3)))}{((6 \times ((1^7) + 4)) - 9)} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (1 + (7 - (4 - 9))))}{(2 - ((0 \times 58) - 3))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - ((5 \times 8) - 3)))}{(2 - (0 - ((5 + 8) \times 3)))} := \frac{(2 - (0 - ((5 + 8) \times 3)))}{(6 + ((17^4) \times 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 + ((17^4) \times 9))}{(2 - (0 - (5 \times (8 + 3))))} := \frac{((6 \times (17 + 4)) - 9)}{(2 - (0 - (5 \times (8 - 3))))} := \frac{(6 + ((17 - 4) \times 9))}{(2 - (0 - (5 + (8 + 3))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 + (174 - 9))}{(2 - (0 - (5 + (8 - 3))))} := \frac{((6 + (1 \times (7 - 4))) \times 9)}{(2 - (0 - (5 + 83)))} := \frac{(6 \times ((17^4) \times 9))}{(2 - (0 - (58 + 3)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (1 \times (7 + (4 - 9))))}{(2 - (0 \times (5 - 83)))} := \frac{(6 \times (((1^7) + 4) \times 9))}{(2 - (0 - 583))} := \frac{(6 + (174 + 9))}{(2 \times ((0 - (5 - 8)) ^ 3))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (174^9))}{(2 \times ((0 \times 5) + (8 \times 3)))} := \frac{(6 + 1749)}{(2 \times ((0 \times 5) + (8 + 3)))} := \frac{(6 \times (1 \times ((7 - 4) \times 9)))}{(2 \times ((0 \times 5) + (8 - 3)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 - (1 - (7 + 4))) \times 9)}{(2 \times ((0 \times 5) + 83))} := \frac{((6 \times 17) - (4 \times 9))}{(2 \times ((0 \times 58) + 3))} := \frac{(((6 - 1) \times 7) + (4 - 9))}{(2 \times (0 - (5 - (8 \times 3))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (1 \times (74 + 9)))}{(2 \times (0 - (5 - 83)))} := \frac{(6 + (1 \times (7 - (4 - 9))))}{(2 \times (0 + ((5 \times 8) + 3)))} := \frac{(6 + ((1 + (7 + 4)) \times 9))}{(2 \times (0 + ((5 \times 8) - 3)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((6 \times (1 + 7)) + 4) \times 9)}{(2 \times (0 + (5 \times (8 \times 3))))} := \frac{(6 \times (1 - (7 - 49)))}{(2 \times (0 + (5 + (8 \times 3))))} := \frac{(6 \times (1 \times ((7 \times 4) + 9)))}{(2 \times (0 + (5 + (8 + 3))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 + (1 \times 74)) \times 9)}{(2 \times (0 + (5 + (8 - 3))))} := \frac{((61 \times (7 - 4)) - 9)}{2^{-05+8+3}} := \frac{(6 - (1 - (7 \times (4 + 9))))}{(2 + ((0 - (5 - 8)) ^ 3))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times ((17^4) + 9))}{(2 + (0 - ((5 - 8) \times 3)))} := \frac{((61 \times (7 - 4)) + 9)}{(2 + (0 - (5 - (8 \times 3))))} := \frac{((6 \times (17 - 4)) + 9)}{(2 + (0 - (5 - (8 + 3))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 + (1 \times ((7 - 4) \times 9)))}{(20 - (5 + (8 + 3)))} := \frac{(6 + (1 + (7 + 49)))}{(20 - (5 - 83))} := \frac{(6 - ((1 - (7 - 4)) \times 9))}{(20 \times (5 + (8 - 3)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (1 \times (7 + (4 - 9))))}{(20 + (5 \times (8 + 3)))} := \frac{(6 \times ((1^7) \times 49))}{(20 + (5 \times 83))} := \frac{(6 \times (1 + ((7 + 4) \times 9)))}{(20 + (58 + 3))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 \times (1 \times (7 - 4))) + 9)}{(205 + (8 - 3))} := \frac{((6 \times (1 + (7 - 4))) + 9)}{2058 + 3} := \frac{((6 + (17 + 4)) \times 9)}{2058 - 3} \\
 &:= \frac{(617 + (4 + 9))}{6174 + 9} := \frac{6174 + 9}{6174 + 9} := \frac{6174 - 9}{6174 - 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{35148}{70296} &:= \frac{(((3 \times 5) - 1) \times 48)}{(7 \times (0 + (2 \times 96)))} &:= \frac{((3 \times (5 + (1^4))) + 8)}{((7^{02}) + (9 - 6))} &:= \frac{((3 \times (5 - 1)) + 48)}{((7 \times (0 + (2 \times 9))) - 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times 51) - 48)}{(7 \times (0 + (2 \times (9 + 6))))} &:= \frac{((3^{5-1^4}) + 8)}{(70 + (2 \times (9 \times 6)))} &:= \frac{((3^{5 \times 1}) - (4 + 8))}{(7 \times (0 + ((2 + 9) \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3^5 \times 1^4) \times 8)}{((70 + 2) \times (9 \times 6))} &:= \frac{((3^{5-1}) - (4 + 8))}{(((7 \times (0 + 2)) + 9) \times 6)} &:= \frac{((3^5) + (1 - 48))}{(7 \times (0 + (2 + (9 \times 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 + (5 + 1)) \times (4 \times 8))}{(70 + ((2^9) - 6))} &:= \frac{((3 + (5 + 1)) \times 48)}{((7 - (0 - 2)) \times 96)} &:= \frac{((3 + (5 - 1)) \times 48)}{(7 \times ((0 \times 2) + 96))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 + 5) \times (1 + (4 \times 8)))}{((70 + (2 \times 9)) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(3 - (5 - (1 - (4 - 8))))}{(7 - (0 - (2 - (9 - 6))))} &:= \frac{(3 - (5 - (1 \times (4 + 8))))}{(7 + (0 - (2 - (9 + 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (5 - (1 + (4 \times 8))))}{(70 - (2^{9-6}))} &:= \frac{(3 - (5 - (1 + 48)))}{(70 + ((2 \times 9) + 6))} &:= \frac{(3 - (5 \times ((1^4) - 8)))}{(70 + (2 \times (9 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (5 \times ((1 - 4) \times 8)))}{((70 - 29) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(3 - (5 \times (1 \times (4 - 8))))}{((7^{02}) - (9 - 6))} &:= \frac{(3 - (5 + ((1 - 4) \times 8)))}{((70 \times 2) - 96)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (5 + (1 - (4 \times 8))))}{(70 - ((2 \times 9) - 6))} &:= \frac{(3 - (5 + (1 \times (4 - 8))))}{(7 + ((0 \times 2) - (9 - 6)))} &:= \frac{(3 - (5 + (1 + (4 - 8))))}{(7 + (0 - (2 + (9 - 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times ((5 \times (1 \times 4)) + 8))}{(7 \times (0 + ((2 \times 9) + 6)))} &:= \frac{(3 \times ((5 + (1 + 4)) \times 8))}{((7 + (0 - 2)) \times 96)} &:= \frac{(3 \times (5 - (1 - (4 \times 8))))}{((7 - (0 - 29)) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (5 - (1 - (4 + 8))))}{((7 - ((0 \times 2) - 9)) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(3 \times (5 - (1 \times (4 - 8))))}{(3 \times (5 - (1 \times (4 - 8))))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (5 - (1 - 48)))}{(3 \times (5 - (1 - 48)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (5 \times ((1^4) + 8)))}{((7 + (0 - 2)) \times (9 \times 6))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (5 \times (1 - (4 - 8))))}{((7 \times (0 \times 2)) + (9 \times 6))} &:= \frac{3 \times 5 \times 1^{48}}{((70 - (2 \times 9)) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (5^{1^4+8}))}{(((7 + (0 - 2))^9) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(3 \times (5 + ((1^4) + 8)))}{((7 - (0 - (2 \times 9))) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(3 \times (5 + (1 + (4 + 8))))}{((7 - (0 - (2 + 9))) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (5 + (1 + (4 - 8))))}{(7 - (0 - (2 + (9 - 6))))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (51 \times (4 + 8)))}{((70 - 2) \times (9 \times 6))} &:= \frac{(3 \times (51 + (4 + 8)))}{(7 \times ((0 \times 2) + (9 \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (51 + 48))}{((70 + 29) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(3^{5+1+4-8})}{(70 + (2 - (9 \times 6)))} &:= \frac{(3 + ((5 - 1) \times (4 \times 8)))}{(70 + (2 \times 96))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (5 - ((1^4)^8))}{(70 - (2 + (9 \times 6)))} &:= \frac{(3 + (5 - ((1 - 4) \times 8)))}{((7^{02}) + (9 + 6))} &:= \frac{(3 + (5 - (1 - (4 \times 8))))}{(70 + (2^{9-6}))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (5 - (1 \times (4 - 8))))}{(7 - (0 - (2 + (9 + 6))))} &:= \frac{(3 + (5 - (1 + (4 - 8))))}{(7 - ((0 \times 2) - (9 + 6)))} &:= \frac{(3 + (5 - (1 - 48)))}{(((7 \times (0 + 2)) + 96)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (5 \times ((1^4) \times 8)))}{((70 \times 2) - (9 \times 6))} &:= \frac{(3 + (5 \times (1 - (4 - 8))))}{(7 \times (0 + (2^{9-6})))} &:= \frac{(3 + (5 \times (1 \times (4 + 8))))}{(70 + (2 + (9 \times 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (5 \times (1 \times 48)))}{((7 - (0 - 2)) \times (9 \times 6))} &:= \frac{(3 + (5 \times (1 + (4 + 8))))}{(70 + ((2 + 9) \times 6))} &:= \frac{(3 + (5 + ((1^4) + 8)))}{((7^{02}) - (9 + 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (5 + (1 \times (4 + 8))))}{((7 \times (0 - 2)) + (9 \times 6))} &:= \frac{(3 + (5 + (1 \times (4 - 8))))}{(7 + (0 - (2 - (9 - 6))))} &:= \frac{(3 + (5 + (1 \times 48)))}{(70 - ((2 - 9) \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (5 + (1 + (4 \times 8))))}{((7 \times (0 - 2)) + 96)} &:= \frac{(3 + (5 + (1 + (4 + 8))))}{(7 \times (0 + (2 \times (9 - 6))))} &:= \frac{(3 + (5 + (1 + (4 - 8))))}{(7 - ((0 \times 2) - (9 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (5 + (14 \times 8)))}{(((7^{02}) - 9) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(3 + (5 + (14 - 8)))}{(70 + ((2 - 9) \times 6))} &:= \frac{(3 + (51 + (4 + 8)))}{((7 \times (0 + (2 \times 9))) + 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (51 + (4 - 8)))}{(70 + (2 \times (9 + 6)))} &:= \frac{(3 + (51 + 48))}{((70 - 2) \times (9 - 6))} &:= \frac{(35 - ((1^4)^8))}{(((7 \times (0 + 2)) + (9 \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(35 - (1 - 48))}{(70 - (2 - 96))} &:= \frac{(35 \times ((1^4) \times 8))}{(70 \times (2^{9-6}))} &:= \frac{(35 \times (1 - (4 - 8)))}{(70 \times (2 + (9 - 6)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(35 \times (1 \times (4 + 8)))}{(70 \times ((2 \times 9) - 6))} &:= \frac{(35 \times (14 - 8))}{(70 \times (2 \times (9 - 6)))} &:= \frac{(35 + (14 \times 8))}{(7 \times (0 - ((2 - 9) \times 6)))} \\ &:= \frac{35 + 148}{70 + 296} &:= \frac{351 + 48}{702 + 96} &:= \frac{351 - 48}{702 - 96} \end{aligned}$$

3.70 76 Equivalent Blocks

► $\frac{23058}{69174}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= \frac{(((2 \times (3 - 0)) - 5)^8)}{(6 + (9 - (1 + (7 + 4))))} &:= \frac{(((2 + (3 - 0)) \times 5) - 8)}{(6 + (9 \times ((1^7) + 4)))} &:= \frac{(((2 + 30) \times 5) + 8)}{(6 \times (9 + (1 + 74)))} \\ &:= \frac{(((2 + 30) \times 5) - 8)}{(6 \times ((9 \times (1 + 7)) + 4))} &:= \frac{((2 - (3 \times (0 - 5))) \times 8)}{(6 \times ((9 + (1 + 7)) \times 4))} &:= \frac{((2 - (3 - 0)) \times (5 - 8))}{(6 - (9 - (1 + (7 + 4))))} \\ &:= \frac{((2 \times (3 - (0 \times 5)))^8)}{((6^{9-1}) \times (7 - 4))} &:= \frac{((2 \times (3 - (0 - 5))) + 8)}{(6 - (9 - (1 + 74)))} &:= \frac{((2 \times (3 \times (0 + 5))) + 8)}{(6 \times (9 - (1 - (7 + 4))))} \\ &:= \frac{((2 \times (3 \times (0 + 5))) - 8)}{(6 \times (9 - (1 - (7 - 4))))} &:= \frac{((2 \times (3 + (0 - 5))) + 8)}{(6 + (9 - (1 \times (7 - 4))))} &:= \frac{((2 \times (30 - 5)) - 8)}{(6 \times (9 + (1 + (7 + 4))))} \\ &:= \frac{((2 \times 30) - (5 \times 8))}{(6 \times (9 + (1^{74})))} &:= \frac{((2 \times 30) + (5 \times 8))}{((69 - (1 - 7)) \times 4)} &:= \frac{((2 \times 30) + (5 + 8))}{((6 - 9) \times (1 - 74))} \\ &:= \frac{((2 \times 30) + 58)}{(6 \times ((9 \times (1 \times 7)) - 4))} &:= \frac{((2^{3-0 \times 5})^8)}{(6 \times (((9 - 1)^7) \times 4))} &:= \frac{((2^{3-0 \times 5}) + 8)}{(6 \times (9 - (1^{74})))} \\ &:= \frac{((2^3 + 0) \times (5 + 8))}{((6 + (9 \times (1 + 7))) \times 4)} &:= \frac{((2^3 + 0) + (5 + 8))}{((6 \times (9 + 1)) + (7 - 4))} &:= \frac{((2 + (3 - (0 \times 5))) \times 8)}{(6 \times (9 + (1 \times (7 + 4))))} \\ &:= \frac{((2 + (3 - (0 - 5))) \times 8)}{(6 \times ((9 + (1^7)) \times 4))} &:= \frac{((2 + (3 - 0)) \times (5 + 8))}{(6 + (9 \times (17 + 4)))} &:= \frac{((2 + (30 - 5)) \times 8)}{(6 \times (9 \times (1 + (7 + 4))))} \\ &:= \frac{((2 + 3)^{-05+8})}{(((6 \times 9) - 1) \times 7) + 4)} &:= \frac{((23 - (0 - 5)) \times 8)}{(6 + (9 \times (1 \times 74)))} &:= \frac{((2 - 30) \times (5 - 8))}{((69 + (1 - 7)) \times 4)} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - ((3 \times (0 \times 5)) - 8))}{(6 \times (9 - (1 + (7 - 4))))} &:= \frac{(2 - ((3 \times (0 - 5)) + 8))}{(2 - ((3 \times (0 - 5)) + 8))} &:= \frac{(2 - ((3 \times (0 - 5)) - 8))}{((6 + 9) \times ((1^7) + 4))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (3 \times ((0 \times 5) - 8)))}{(6 \times (9 + (1 + (7 - 4))))} &:= \frac{(2 - (3 \times (0 - (5 + 8))))}{(2 - (3 \times (0 \times 58)))} &:= \frac{(2 - (3 \times (0 \times 58)))}{6 \times (9 - 1 - 7)^4} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (3 \times (0 - 58)))}{(6 \times (91 - (7 - 4)))} &:= \frac{(2 - (3 + ((0 \times 5) - 8)))}{(6 - (9 + ((1 - 7) \times 4)))} &:= \frac{(2 - (3 + (0 - 58)))}{(6 - (9 - 174))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 - (30 \times (5 - 8)))}{((6 + (9 \times (1 \times 7))) \times 4)} &:= \frac{(2 - (30 - 58))}{(6 + (9 + (1 + 74)))} &:= \frac{(2 \times ((3 - (0 - 5)) \times 8))}{(6 \times ((9 + (1 \times 7)) \times 4))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times ((3 \times (0 + 5)) - 8))}{(6 \times (9 + (1 - (7 - 4))))} &:= \frac{(2 \times ((30 + 5) \times 8))}{(6 \times ((9 + 1) \times (7 \times 4)))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (3 - (0 - (5 \times 8))))}{(6 + (9 \times (1 \times (7 \times 4))))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 \times (3 - (0 - (5 + 8))))}{(2 \times (3 - (0 \times 58)))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (3 - (0 \times 58)))}{(2 \times (3 - (0 \times 58)))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (3 \times ((0 \times 5) + 8)))}{6^{9-1 \times 7} \times 4} \\ &:= \frac{(6 - (9 \times (1 - (7 + 4))))}{(2 \times (3 \times (0 - (5 - 8))))} &:= \frac{(6 + (9 + (1 \times (7 - 4))))}{2 \times 3^{0 \times 5 + 8}} &:= \frac{(6 - (9 - 174))}{(2 \times (3^{-05+8}))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times (9 \times (1^{74})))}{(2 \times (3 + (0 - (5 - 8))))} &:= \frac{(6 \times (9 \times (1 + (7 - 4))))}{(2 \times (30 - (5 + 8)))} &:= \frac{(6 \times (9 \times (1 \times (7 - 4))))}{(2 \times (30 \times (5 \times 8)))} \\ &:= \frac{(6 \times (9 - (1 \times (7 - 4))))}{(2 \times (30 + (5 \times 8)))} &:= \frac{(6 \times (91 - 74))}{2^3 + 0 \times 58} &:= \frac{((6 - 9) \times (1 - (7^4)))}{2^{3-05+8}} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + ((3 - (0 - 5)) \times 8))}{(6 \times (9 - ((1 - 7) \times 4)))} &:= \frac{(6 - (9 \times (1 - (7 - 4))))}{(2 + ((3^{05}) + 8))} &:= \frac{(6 \times ((9 - (1^7)) \times 4))}{(2 + ((30 \times 5) + 8))} \\ &:= \frac{(2 + ((3 - (0 - 5)) \times 8))}{(6 \times (9 - ((1 - 7) \times 4)))} &:= \frac{(69 \times (1 \times (7 + 4)))}{(6 \times (91 - (7 + 4)))} &:= \frac{(6 \times (91 - (7 + 4)))}{(6 \times (91 - (7 + 4)))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(2 + (3 - ((0 \times 5) - 8)))}{(6 + (9 - ((1 - 7) \times 4)))} := \frac{(2 + (3 - (0 \times 58)))}{(6 + (9 \times (1^{74})))} := \frac{(2 + (3 - (0 - 58)))}{(6 + (9 + 174))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (3 \times (0 - (5 - 8))))}{(6 + (9 \times (1 \times (7 - 4))))} := \frac{(2 + (3^{-05+8}))}{(6 + ((9 + (1 - 7))^4))} := \frac{(2 + (30 - (5 + 8)))}{((6 \times (9 \times 1)) + (7 - 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (30 - (5 - 8)))}{(6 + (9 \times (1 \times (7 + 4))))} := \frac{(2 + (30 + (5 \times 8)))}{(6 \times (9 \times (1 + (7 - 4))))} := \frac{(2 + (30 + 58))}{(6 \times (9 \times ((1^7) + 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (305 - 8))}{(69 \times (17 - 4))} := \frac{(2 + 3058)}{(6 + 9174)} := \frac{(23 - ((0 \times 5) - 8))}{(69 - ((1 - 7) \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(23 - (0 - (5 + 8)))}{(6 + (91 + (7 + 4)))} := \frac{(23 - (0 \times 58))}{(6 + (91 - (7 \times 4)))} := \frac{(23 - (0 - 58))}{(69 + 174)} \\
 &:= \frac{(23 \times (0 - (5 - 8)))}{(69 \times (1 \times (7 - 4)))} := \frac{(23 + ((0 \times 5) - 8))}{((6 + (9 \times 1)) \times (7 - 4))} := \frac{(230 + (5 - 8))}{(6 + (9 \times (1 + 74)))} \\
 &:= \frac{230 + 58}{6^{9+1-7} \times 4}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.71 77 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{32709}{65418} &:= \frac{(((3 \times 2) + (7 - 0)) \times 9)}{((6 + (5 \times 4)) \times (1 + 8))} := \frac{(((3^2) \times 70) - 9)}{((65 + 4) \times 18)} := \frac{(((3 - 2)^7 + 0) + 9)}{((6 \times (5 - (4 - 1))) + 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 - (2 \times 7)) \times (0 - 9))}{(6 \times (5 - (4 \times (1 - 8))))} := \frac{((3 - (2 - 70)) \times 9)}{(6 \times ((5 \times 41) + 8))} := \frac{((3 \times (2 \times (7 - 0))) + 9)}{(3 \times (2 \times (7 - 0))) + 9)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (2 \times (7 - 0))) - 9)}{(6 + (5 \times (4 + (1 \times 8))))} := \frac{((3 \times (2^7 + 0)) - 9)}{(6 \times (5^{4-1^8}))} := \frac{((3 \times (2 + (7 - 0))) + 9)}{(6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 1)) - 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (2 + (7 - 0))) - 9)}{6^{5-4+1^8}} := \frac{((3 \times 2)^{7+0 \times 9})}{((6^5) \times (4 \times 18))} := \frac{((3 \times 2) + (7 - (0 \times 9)))}{((3 \times 2) + (70 - 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times 2) + (7 - (0 - 9)))}{(6 + (5 + (41 - 8)))} := \frac{((3 \times 2) + (7 + (0 - 9)))}{(6 + (5 - (4 - (1^8))))} := \frac{((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 1)) + 8)}{((3 \times 2) + (70 - 9))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times 2) + 709)}{(65 \times (4 + 18))} := \frac{((3^2) - (7 - (0 \times 9)))}{(6 - (5 - (4 - (1^8))))} := \frac{((3^2) - (7 + (0 - 9)))}{(6 + (5 + (4 - (1 - 8))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3^2) \times (7 - (0 \times 9)))}{(6 + (5 \times ((4 - 1) \times 8)))} := \frac{((3^2) \times (7 - (0 - 9)))}{6^{5-4+1} \times 8} := \frac{((3^2) \times (70 - 9))}{((65 - 4) \times 18)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 + (2 \times (7 - 0))) \times 9)}{((6 \times 54) - 18)} := \frac{((3 + (2 + (7 - 0))) \times 9)}{(6 \times (54 - 18))} := \frac{((3 + (27 - 0)) \times 9)}{((6 + 54) \times (1 + 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 + 2) \times (7 \times (0 + 9)))}{(6 + ((5^4) - (1^8)))} := \frac{((3 - 2) \times (70 + 9))}{((6 \times (5 \times (4 + 1))) + 8)} := \frac{((3 - 2) \times (70 - 9))}{((6 \times ((5 \times 4) - 1)) + 8)} \\
 &:= \frac{((32 \times (7 - 0)) - 9)}{(6 + ((54 - 1) \times 8))} := \frac{((32 + (7 - 0)) \times 9)}{(6 \times ((5^{4-1} - 8))} := \frac{((3 - 27) \times (0 - 9))}{(6 \times ((5 + (4 \times 1)) \times 8))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - ((2 - (7 - 0)) \times 9))}{(6 \times (5 + (4 - (1 - 8))))} := \frac{(3 - (2 - (7 - (0 \times 9))))}{(6 + (5 + (4 + (1^8))))} := \frac{(3 - (2 - (7 - (0 - 9))))}{(6 - (5 - (41 - 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (2 - (7 \times (0 \times 9))))}{(3 - (2 - (7 - (0 \times 9))))} := \frac{(3 - (2 + (7 \times (0 - 9))))}{(3 - (2 + (7 + (0 - 9))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((6 - 5)^4) + (1^8))}{(3 - (27 \times (0 - 9)))} := \frac{((6 \times (5 \times (4 + 1))) + 8)}{(3 \times ((2 \times (7 - 0)) + 9))} := \frac{6^{5-4 \times 1^8}}{(3 \times ((2 + (7 - 0))^9))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (27 \times (0 - 9)))}{(6 + (54 \times (1 + 8)))} := \frac{(3 \times ((5 \times (4 - 1)) + 8))}{(6 \times ((5 + 4) \times (1 + 8)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times ((2 - 7) \times (0 - 9)))}{(6 \times (5 + ((4 + 1) \times 8)))} := \frac{(3 \times (2 - (7 \times (0 \times 9))))}{(6 \times (5 - (4 - (1^8))))} := \frac{(3 \times (2 - (7 \times (0 - 9))))}{(6 \times (5 \times (4 + (1 + 8))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{(3 \times (2 - (7 + (0 - 9))))}{(6 + (5 + (4 + (1 + 8))))} := \frac{(3 \times (2 \times (7 - (0 - 9))))}{((65 - 41) \times 8)} := \frac{(3 \times (2 + (7 - (0 \times 9))))}{(6 \times (5 + (4 \times (1^8))))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 \times (2 + (7 - (0 - 9))))}{(6 \times (5 + (4 + (1 + 8))))} := \frac{(3 \times (2 + (70 \times 9)))}{(6 \times ((5^4) - (1 - 8)))} := \frac{(3 \times (2 + (70 + 9)))}{(6 \times ((5 + 4) \times (1 + 8)))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 \times (2 + (70 - 9)))}{(6 \times (54 + (1 + 8)))} := \frac{3^2 + 7 \times 0 \times 9}{(6 + ((5 \times (4 \times 1)) - 8))} := \frac{(3^{2-7+09})}{(6 \times (5 + (4 + 18)))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 + ((2 \times (7 - 0)) + 9))}{((6 \times (5 + (4 + 1))) - 8)} := \frac{(3 + ((2 \times 70) - 9))}{((6 \times (5 + 41)) - 8)} := \frac{(3 + ((2^7 + 0) + 9))}{((6 \times 5) + (4 + 1)) \times 8} \\
 & := \frac{(3 + (2 - (7 \times (0 \times 9))))}{(((6 - 5)^4) + (1 + 8))} := \frac{(3 + (2 - (7 + (0 - 9))))}{(6 + (5 + (4 - (1^8))))} := \frac{(3 + (2 \times (7 - (0 - 9))))}{(6 + ((5 + (4 - 1)) \times 8))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 + (2 \times (70 + 9)))}{((6 \times (54 + 1)) - 8)} := \frac{(3 + (2^{7+0 \times 9}))}{(6 + ((5 - (4 - 1))^8))} := \frac{(3 + (2 + (7 - (0 - 9))))}{(6 \times ((5 \times (4 - 1)) - 8))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 + (2 + (70 + 9)))}{(6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 1)) + 8))} := \frac{(3 + 2709)}{((6 + 5) \times (4 + (1 \times 8)))} := \frac{(3 + (27 - (0 \times 9)))}{(6 \times (5 + (4 + (1^8))))} \\
 & := \frac{(6 + ((5 + (4 \times 1)) \times 8))}{(32 - (7 - (0 - 9)))} := \frac{(6 + 5418)}{(32 - (7 \times (0 \times 9)))} := \frac{(6 - (5 - (41 + 8)))}{(32 - (7 + (0 - 9)))} \\
 & := \frac{((6 - (5 - (4 - 1))) \times 8)}{(32 \times (7 - (0 \times 9)))} := \frac{((6 + (5 - (4 - 1))) \times 8)}{(32 \times (70 + 9))} := \frac{((6 \times (5 + (4 + 1))) + 8)}{(32 + (70 + 9))} \\
 & := \frac{((6 \times 5) + 418)}{(32 + (70 - 9))} := \frac{((6 + ((5^4) + 1)) \times 8)}{327 - 0 \times 9} := \frac{(6 \times (5 + (4 \times (1 \times 8))))}{327 \times 09} \\
 & := \frac{(6 + (5 \times (4 \times (1 + 8))))}{327 + 09} := \frac{654 \times (1^8)}{327 - 09} := \frac{654 \times (1 + 8)}{654 - 18} \\
 & := \frac{327 + 09}{654 + 18} := \frac{327 - 09}{654 - 18}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.72 79 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{20793}{41586} & := \frac{(((2 \times (0 + 7)) + 9) \times 3)}{((4 - 1) \times ((5 \times 8) + 6))} := \frac{(((2 \times (0 + 7)) - 9)^3)}{((4 \times (1 - (5 - 8))) - 6)} := \frac{(((20 + 7) \times 9) - 3)}{((4 + (1 + 5)) \times (8 \times 6))} \\
 & := \frac{((2 - ((0 \times 7) - 9)) \times 3)}{((4 + (15 - 8)) \times 6)} := \frac{((2 - (0 - (7 \times 9))) \times 3)}{((4 + 1) \times ((5 + 8) \times 6))} := \frac{((2 - (0 - (7 + 9))) \times 3)}{((4 + (1 + (5 + 8))) \times 6)} \\
 & := \frac{((2 - (0 - (7 + 9)))^3)}{(((4 - 1)^5) \times (8 \times 6))} := \frac{((2 - (0 - 7)) \times (9 + 3))}{(4 \times (1 + (5 + (8 \times 6))))} := \frac{((2 - (0 - 79)) \times 3)}{((4 \times (15 \times 8)) + 6)} \\
 & := \frac{((2 \times (0 \times 7)) + 93)}{((4 \times ((1 + 5) \times 8)) - 6)} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + (7 \times 9))) + 3)}{((4 - (1 - (5 \times 8))) \times 6)} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + (7 + 9)))^3)}{(4 \times (1 + (5 + (8 - 6))))} \\
 & := \frac{((2 \times (0 + (7 + 9))) + 3)}{((4 + (1^5)) \times (8 + 6))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + (7 + 9))) - 3)}{((2 \times (0 + (7 + 9))) + 3)} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + 7)) + (9 \times 3))}{(4 + (1 \times ((5 + 8) \times 6)))} \\
 & := \frac{((2 \times (0 + 7)) + (9 - 3))}{(4 \times (1 \times (5 \times (8 - 6))))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 + 7)) + 93)}{(4 + (15 \times (8 + 6)))} := \frac{((2 \times (0 - 7)) + (9 \times 3))}{((4 \times ((1^5) \times 8)) - 6)} \\
 & := \frac{((2 \times (0 - 7)) + 93)}{((4 \times (1 + (5 \times 8))) - 6)} := \frac{((2^{0 \times 7 + 9})^3)}{((4 \times (1 \times 5)) \times (8^6))} := \frac{((2^{07}) - (9 - 3))}{(4 + (1 \times (5 \times (8 \times 6))))} \\
 & := \frac{((2^{07}) \times (9 - 3))}{((4 \times (1 - (5 - 8))) \times 6)} := \frac{((2^{07}) + (9 + 3))}{(4 \times (1 \times (5 \times (8 + 6))))} := \frac{((20 - (7 - 9)) \times 3)}{(41 + (5 + 86))} \\
 & := \frac{((20 \times 7) - (9 \times 3))}{((4 \times (1 \times 58)) - 6)} := \frac{((20 \times 7) - (9 + 3))}{(4 \times (1 + (5 - (8 - 6))))} := \frac{((20 \times 7) + (9 - 3))}{(4 + ((1 + 5) \times (8 \times 6)))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((20 \times 7) - 93)}{(4 - (1 - (5 + 86)))} &:= \frac{((20 + 7) \times (9^3))}{(((4 - (1^5))^8) \times 6)} &:= \frac{((20 + 7) \times (9 - 3))}{((41 + (5 + 8)) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{((20 + 79) \times 3)}{((41 + 58) \times 6)} &:= \frac{((20 - 7) \times (9 + 3))}{(4 \times (1 \times ((5 + 8) \times 6)))} &:= \frac{((207 + 9) \times 3)}{((41 - 5)^{8-6})} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - ((0 \times 7) - (9 + 3)))}{(4 - (1 - (5^{8-6})))} &:= \frac{(2 - ((0 \times 79) - 3))}{(4 - (1 - (5 + (8 - 6))))} &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - ((7 + 9) \times 3)))}{(4 \times (1 \times (5^{8-6})))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (7 - (9 - 3))))}{(4 - (1 - (5 - (8 - 6))))} &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (7 \times (9 - 3))))}{(4 + ((1 + (5 + 8)) \times 6))} &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (7 + (9 \times 3))))}{((4 + ((1^5) \times 8)) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (7 + (9 + 3))))}{((4 - (1 \times (5 - 8))) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (7 + (9 - 3))))}{(4 + (1 + (5^{8-6})))} &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - (79 - 3)))}{(4 + (158 - 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 - (0 \times (7 - 93)))}{(4 \times (1^{586}))} &:= \frac{(2 - (0 - 793))}{(4 + 1586)} &:= \frac{(2 \times ((0 - (7 - 9))^3))}{(4 \times (1 + (5 + (8 - 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times ((0 \times 7) + (9 + 3)))}{(4 + (1 - (5 - (8 \times 6))))} &:= \frac{(2 \times ((0 \times 7) + 93))}{((4 + (1 \times 58)) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(2 \times ((0 \times 79) + 3))}{(4 \times (1 \times (5 - (8 - 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 - ((7 - 9) \times 3)))}{(4 + (1 + (5 + (8 + 6))))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 - (7 - (9 \times 3))))}{(4 \times (1 + (5 + (8 + 6))))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 - (7 - (9 + 3))))}{((4 + (1 + 5)) \times (8 - 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 - (7 - 93)))}{(4 \times ((1^5) \times 86))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + ((7 \times 9) + 3)))}{((4 + (1 \times (5 \times 8))) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + ((7 \times 9) - 3)))}{((4 + (1^5)) \times (8 \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + ((7 + 9) \times 3)))}{(4 \times ((1^5) \times (8 \times 6)))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + ((7 + 9)^3))}{(4 \times (1 \times (5 + (8 - 6))))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (7 \times (9 + 3))))}{(4 \times ((1 + (5 + 8)) \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (7 \times (9 - 3))))}{(4 + (158 + 6))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (7^9-3)))}{(4 \times ((15 - 8)^6))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (7 + (9 \times 3))))}{(4 \times (1 \times ((5 \times 8) - 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (7 + (9 + 3))))}{(4 \times (1 \times (5 + (8 + 6))))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (7 + (9 - 3))))}{(4 \times (15 - (8 - 6)))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (7 + 93)))}{((4 \times (1 \times 5))^{8-6})} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (79 + 3)))}{(4 \times (1 - (5 - 86)))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (79 + 3)))}{(4 \times (1 + (5 - (8 - 6))))} &:= \frac{(2 \times (0 + (79 + 3)))}{(4 \times (1 \times (5 - (8 - 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (0 - (7 - (9 \times 3))))}{(4 \times (1 + (5 \times (8 - 6))))} &:= \frac{(2 + (0 - (7 - (9 + 3))))}{(4 + (1 \times (5 \times (8 - 6))))} &:= \frac{(2 + (0 - (7 - (9 - 3))))}{(4 + (1 - (5 - (8 - 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2 + (0 - (7 - 93)))}{(4 \times (1 - (5 - (8 \times 6))))} &:= \frac{(20 - (7 - (9 + 3)))}{((4 \times (1 + (5 + 8))) - 6)} &:= \frac{(20 - (7 - (9 - 3)))}{(4 + (1 \times ((5 \times 8) - 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{(20 - (7 - 93))}{(4 \times (1 \times (5 + (8 \times 6))))} &:= \frac{(20 \times (7 + (9 - 3)))}{(4 + ((1 + 5) \times 86))} &:= \frac{(20 + (7 \times (9 + 3)))}{(4 \times (1 \times (58 - 6)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(2079 + 3)}{((4 + ((1^5) + 8)) \times 6)} &:= \frac{(2079 + 3)}{(4158 + 6)} &:= \frac{(207 - 93)}{((41 + (5 - 8)) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{(2079 - 3)}{(4158 - 6)}
 \end{aligned}$$

30792
 61584

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((3 - (0 - 7)) \times 9) + 2)}{((6 + (1 \times (5 \times 8))) \times 4)} &:= \frac{(((3 \times (0 + 7)) - 9) \times 2)}{(6 \times (1 - (5 - (8 + 4))))} &:= \frac{(((30 - 7) \times 9) - 2)}{(((6 + 1) \times 58) + 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 - (0 - (7 \times 9))) \times 2)}{(6 \times (1 \times ((5 \times 8) + 4)))} &:= \frac{((3 - (0 - (7 + 9))) \times 2)}{((6 + (1 \times (5 + 8))) \times 4)} &:= \frac{((3 - (0 - 7)) \times (9 \times 2))}{(6 \times (1 \times (5 \times (8 + 4))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 - (0 - 7)) \times (9 + 2))}{((6 - 1) \times ((5 \times 8) + 4))} &:= \frac{((3 - (0 - 7)) \times (9 - 2))}{(61 - (5 - 84))} &:= \frac{((3 - (0 - 79)) \times 2)}{(((6 \times 15) - 8) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times ((0 \times 7) + 9)) + 2)}{(6 + (1 \times ((5 + 8) \times 4)))} &:= \frac{(((3 \times (0 - (7 - 9)))^2)}{((6 - (1 - (5 + 8))) \times 4)} &:= \frac{((3 \times (0 - (7 - 9))) + 2)}{(6 + (1 + (5 + (8 - 4))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (0 - (7 - 9))) - 2)}{(6 + (1 + (5 - (8 - 4))))} &:= \frac{((3 \times (0 \times 79)) + 2)}{(6 - (1 + (5 - (8 - 4))))} &:= \frac{((3 \times (0 + (7 + 9))) + 2)}{(((6 + (1 + 5)) \times 8) + 4)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (0 + (7 + 9))) - 2)}{(((6 + (1 + 5)) \times 8) - 4)} := \frac{((3 \times (0 + 7)) + (9 \times 2))}{(6 \times (1 - ((5 - 8) \times 4)))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 + 7)) + (9 + 2))}{((6 + (1 - 5)) \times (8 \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (0 - 7)) + (9^2))}{(6 \times (1 \times (5 \times (8 - 4))))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 - 7)) + 92)}{((6 \times (15 + 8)) + 4)} := \frac{((3^{-07+9}) \times 2)}{(6 \times (1 + (5 - (8 - 4))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3^{-07+9}) + 2)}{(6 - (1 - (5 + (8 + 4))))} := \frac{((3 + (0 - (7 - 9))) \times 2)}{((6 \times (1 - (5 - 8))) - 4)} := \frac{((3 + (0 - (7 - 9)))^2)}{(6 + (1 \times ((5 \times 8) + 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((30 - (7 + 9))^2)}{(((6 \times 15) + 8) \times 4)} := \frac{((30 \times 7) - (9 \times 2))}{((6 + (1 + 5)) \times (8 \times 4))} := \frac{((30 \times 7) + (9 - 2))}{((6 + 1) \times (58 + 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{((30 + (7 \times 9)) \times 2)}{((30 + (7 - 9)) \times 2)} := \frac{((30 + (7 - 9)) \times 2)}{((30 + (7 - 9)) \times 2)} := \frac{(3 - ((0 \times 79) - 2))}{(3 - ((0 \times 79) - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (1 \times (58 + 4)))}{(3 - (0 - ((7 + 9) \times 2)))} := \frac{(((6 \times (1 + 5)) - 8) \times 4)}{(3 - (0 - (7 \times (9 + 2))))} := \frac{(6 + ((1^5) \times (8 - 4)))}{(3 - (0 - (7 + (9 \times 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(61 + (5 + (8 - 4)))}{(3 - (0 - (7 + (9 + 2))))} := \frac{(6 + (158 - 4))}{(3 - (0 - (7 + (9 - 2))))} := \frac{((6 + ((1^5) \times 8)) \times 4)}{(3 - (0 - (7 + 92)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 - (1 - (5 + (8 \times 4))))}{(3 - (0 - (79 + 2)))} := \frac{(6 + (1 - (5 - (8 \times 4))))}{(3 - (0 \times (7 - 92)))} := \frac{(((6 - 1) \times (5 \times 8)) + 4)}{(3 - (0 - 792))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (1 - (5 - (8 \times 4))))}{(3 \times ((0 \times 7) + 92))} := \frac{(6 \times (1^{584}))}{(3 \times ((0 \times 79) + 2))} := \frac{(6 + 1584)}{(3 \times (0 - (7 - (9 \times 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times ((15 + 8) \times 4))}{(3 \times (0 - (7 - (9^2))))} := \frac{(6 \times (1 + (5 - (8 - 4))))}{(3 \times (0 - (7 - (9 + 2))))} := \frac{(6 + (1 \times (5 \times (8 + 4))))}{(3 \times (0 - (7 - 92)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((61 - 5) \times 8) - 4)}{((61 - 5) \times 8) - 4} := \frac{(6 + (1 + (5 + (8 + 4))))}{(6 + (1 + (5 + (8 + 4))))} := \frac{(6 \times ((1^5) + 84))}{(6 \times ((1^5) + 84))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + ((7 \times 9) - 2)))}{(6 \times (1 + (5 \times (8 + 4))))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + ((7 + 9) \times 2)))}{(6 \times ((1^5) \times (8 \times 4)))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + ((7 + 9)^2))}{(6 \times ((1 - (5 - 8))^4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (7 \times (9 - 2))))}{((6 - 1) \times 58) + 4} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (7 + (9 \times 2))))}{(3 \times (0 + (7 + (9 \times 2))))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (7 + (9 + 2))))}{(3 \times (0 + (7 + (9 + 2))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (7 + (9 - 2))))}{(6 - (1 + (5 - 84)))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (7 + 92)))}{(6 \times (15 + 84))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (79 + 2)))}{(6 + (15 \times (8 \times 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{3^{0 \times 79 + 2}}{(6 - (1 \times ((5 - 8) \times 4)))} := \frac{3^{-07 + 9 + 2}}{(6 - ((1 - (5 \times 8)) \times 4))} := \frac{(3 + ((0 \times 79) - 2))}{(6 - ((1^5) \times (8 - 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 + (0 - (7 - (9 \times 2))))}{((6 \times (1 - (5 - 8))) + 4)} := \frac{(3 + (0 - (7 - (9 + 2))))}{(6 - (1 - (5 + (8 - 4))))} := \frac{(3 + (0 - (7 - 92)))}{(((6 \times (1 + 5)) + 8) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(30 - (7 - (9 \times 2)))}{((6 \times (1 \times (5 + 8))) + 4)} := \frac{(30 - (7 - (9 + 2)))}{(6 + (1 \times (58 + 4)))} := \frac{(30 - (7 - (9 - 2)))}{(6 \times (1 + (5 + (8 - 4))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(30 - (7 + (9 - 2)))}{(30 - (7 + (9 - 2)))} := \frac{(30 \times ((7 \times 9) - 2))}{(30 \times ((7 \times 9) - 2))} := \frac{(30 \times (7 \times (9 \times 2)))}{(30 \times (7 \times (9 \times 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 - (1 + (5 - (8 \times 4))))}{(30 \times (7 \times (9 - 2)))} := \frac{(61 \times (5 \times (8 + 4)))}{(30 \times (7 + (9 + 2)))} := \frac{(6 \times (15 \times 84))}{(30 \times (7 + (9 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 + 1) \times (5 \times 84)}{(30 + (7 - (9 \times 2)))} := \frac{(6 \times (15 \times (8 + 4)))}{(30 + (7 - (9 + 2)))} := \frac{((6 - (1 - 5)) \times 84)}{(30 + (7 \times (9 \times 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 \times (15 - 8)) - 4)}{(30 + (7 + (9^2)))} := \frac{((6 + (15 - 8)) \times 4)}{(30 + (7 + (9 + 2)))} := \frac{(6 \times (1 \times ((5 + 8) \times 4)))}{(30 + (7 + (9 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(30 + (7 + (9^2)))}{((6 \times (1 \times (5 \times 8))) - 4)} := \frac{(30 + (7 + (9 + 2)))}{(6 + (1 + (5 + 84)))} := \frac{(30 + (7 + (9 - 2)))}{((6 \times (1 + (5 + 8))) + 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(30 + (79 + 2))}{(6 \times (1 \times (5 + (8 \times 4))))} := \frac{(307 - (9^2))}{(((61 - 5) \times 8) + 4)} := \frac{3079 + 2}{6158 + 4} \\
 &:= \frac{3079 - 2}{6158 - 4}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.73 81 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30927}{61854} &:= \frac{(((3 - (0 - 9)) \times 2) + 7)}{(6 + ((1 + (8 + 5)) \times 4))} := \frac{(((3 - (0 - 9))^2) - 7)}{((6 \times ((1 + 8) \times 5)) + 4)} := \frac{(((3 \times (0 + 9)) - 2) \times 7)}{(6 + ((1 + 85) \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(((30 + 9) \times 2) + 7)}{(6 + ((1 + (8 \times 5)) \times 4))} := \frac{(((30 + 9) \times 2) - 7)}{((6 \times (18 + 5)) + 4)} := \frac{(((30 - 9) \times 2) + 7)}{(6 + ((18 + 5) \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 - ((0 \times 9) - 2)) \times 7)}{(61 + (8 + (5 - 4)))} := \frac{((3 - (0 - (9 + 2))) \times 7)}{((6 \times (1 + 8)) - 5) \times 4} := \frac{((3 - (0 - (9 - 2))) \times 7)}{((6 + (1^8)) \times (5 \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 - (0 - 9)) \times (2 \times 7))}{(6 \times ((1 + (8 + 5)) \times 4))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 \times 9)) - (2 - 7))}{(6 + ((1^{85}) \times 4))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 \times 9)) + (2^7))}{((6 + (1 - (8 - 5)))^4)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (0 \times 9)) + (2 + 7))}{(6 - (1 \times (8 - (5 \times 4))))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 + (9 \times 2))) - 7)}{(6 - (1 - (85 + 4)))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 + (9^2))) + 7)}{(((6 - 1)^{8-5}) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (0 + (9 + 2))) + 7)}{((6 + (1 + (8 + 5))) \times 4)} := \frac{((3 \times (0 + (9 - 2))) + 7)}{((6 + 1) \times (8 \times (5 - 4)))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 + (9 - 2))) - 7)}{((6 + (1^{85})) \times 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (0 + 9)) - (2 \times 7))}{(6 + ((1^8) \times (5 \times 4)))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 + 9)) - (2 + 7))}{(6 \times (1 - (8 - (5 + 4))))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 + 9)) + (2 \times 7))}{((6 \times (1 \times (8 + 5))) + 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (0 + 9)) + (2^7))}{((6 - 1) \times (8 + 54))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 + 9)) + (2 + 7))}{(6 \times (1 \times ((8 - 5) \times 4)))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 + 9)) + (2 - 7))}{(6 + (18 + (5 \times 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{3^{0 \times 9 + 2} \times 7}{3^{0 \times 9 + 2} \times 7} := \frac{3^{0 \times 9 + 2} + 7}{3^{0 \times 9 + 2} + 7} := \frac{3^{0 \times 9 + 2} - 7}{3^{0 \times 9 + 2} - 7} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times ((1^8) + (5 \times 4)))}{((3 + ((0 \times 9) - 2))^7)} := \frac{((6 - (1 - (8 - 5))) \times 4)}{((3 + (0 - 9)) \times (2 - 7))} := \frac{(6 - (1 - (8 - (5 + 4))))}{((30 - (9 + 2)) \times 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 - ((1^{85}) \times 4))}{((30 \times (9 - 2)) + 7)} := \frac{(6 \times (1 + (8 + (5 - 4))))}{((30 \times 9) - (2 \times 7))} := \frac{(6 \times ((1 + 8) \times 5)) - 4}{((30 \times 9) - (2^7))} \\
 &:= \frac{((61 \times 8) - 54)}{((30 + (9 \times 2)) \times 7)} := \frac{((6 \times (1 + 85)) - 4)}{((30 + 9) \times (2 + 7))} := \frac{(((6 + 1) \times (8 \times 5)) + 4)}{((30 + 92) \times 7)} \\
 &:= \frac{(618 + 54)}{((30 - 9) \times (2 + 7))} := \frac{((6 - (1 - 8)) \times 54)}{((30 - 9) \times 27)} := \frac{(61 \times (8 + (5 \times 4)))}{(3 - ((0 \times 9) - (2^7)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 \times (1 + (8 + 54))))}{(3 - ((0 \times 92) - 7))} := \frac{(6 \times (185 + 4))}{(3 - (0 - (9 - (2 - 7))))} := \frac{(6 + ((1 + (8 - 5))^4))}{(3 - (0 - (9 \times (2 + 7))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((6 - (1^{85})) \times 4)}{((6 - (1^{85})) \times 4)} := \frac{(6 + (1 \times (8 + (5 \times 4))))}{(6 + (1 \times (8 + (5 \times 4))))} := \frac{(6 \times (1 \times (8 + (5 \times 4))))}{(6 \times (1 \times (8 + (5 \times 4))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (0 - (9 \times 27)))}{(6 \times (1 + (85 - 4)))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (9 + (2 \times 7))))}{(6 - (1 \times (8 - 54)))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (9 + (2^7))))}{((6 + (1 \times 8)) \times (5 \times 4))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 - (0 - (9 + (2 - 7))))}{(6 + (1 \times (8 \times (5 - 4))))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (9 + 27)))}{(3 - (0 - (9 + 27)))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (92 + 7)))}{(3 - (0 - (92 + 7)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 + (1 \times (8 \times (5 - 4))))}{(3 - (0 \times (9 - 27)))} := \frac{(6 + (1 \times (8 \times (5 + 4))))}{(3 - (0 - 927))} := \frac{((6 + ((1 + 8) \times 5)) \times 4)}{(3 \times ((0 \times 9) + (2 + 7)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times (1^{854}))}{(3 \times (0 - (9 - (2 \times 7))))} := \frac{(6 + 1854)}{(3 \times (0 - (9 \times (2 - 7))))} := \frac{(6 \times (1 + (8 \times (5 - 4))))}{(3 \times (0 - (9 - 27)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(6 \times ((1^{85}) + 4))}{(3 \times (0 + ((9 \times 2) + 7)))} := \frac{(6 \times (1 + ((8 \times 5) + 4)))}{(3 \times (0 + ((9 \times 2) - 7)))} := \frac{(6 \times (1 + (8 + (5 + 4))))}{(3 \times (0 + ((9 - 2) \times 7)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(61 + (85 + 4))}{(3 \times (0 + (9 - (2 - 7))))} := \frac{(((6 + (1 \times 8)) \times 5) - 4)}{(3 \times (0 + (9 \times (2 \times 7))))} := \frac{(6 \times (((1 + 8) \times 5) + 4))}{(3 \times (0 + (9 \times (2 + 7))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((61 - (8 \times 5)) \times 4)}{((61 - (8 \times 5)) \times 4)} := \frac{((6 + (1 \times 8)) \times 54)}{((6 + (1 \times 8)) \times 54)} := \frac{(6 \times (1 \times (85 - 4)))}{(6 \times (1 \times (85 - 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + (9^{2+7})))}{(6 \times ((1 + 8)^{5+4}))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (9 + (2 - 7))))}{(6 + (1 + (8 + (5 + 4))))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (9 + 27)))}{(6 \times (1 \times ((8 \times 5) - 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(3 \times (0 + 927))}{(618 \times (5 + 4))} := \frac{3^{09+2-7}}{(6 - ((1 - (8 \times 5)) \times 4))} := \frac{(3 + (0 - (9 - (2 \times 7))))}{(6 + (1 + (8 + (5 - 4))))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(3 + (0 - (9 - (2^7))))}{((6 \times (1 \times (8 \times 5))) + 4)} := \frac{(3 + (0 - (9 \times (2 - 7))))}{(6 + (1 + (85 + 4)))} := \frac{(3 + (0 - (9 - 27)))}{(6 \times (1 \times (8 - (5 - 4))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(30 \times ((9^2) - 7))}{(6 \times (185 \times 4))} := \frac{(30 \times (9 + (2 \times 7)))}{((61 + 8) \times (5 \times 4))} := \frac{(30 \times (9 + (2 + 7)))}{(6 \times ((1 + 8) \times (5 \times 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(30 \times (9 + 27))}{(6 \times (18 \times (5 \times 4)))} := \frac{(30 + ((9 \times 2) + 7))}{(((6 + 1) \times 8) + 54)} := \frac{(30 + ((9^2) + 7))}{((6 \times (1 \times (8 \times 5))) - 4)} \\
 &:= \frac{(30 + (9 - (2 \times 7)))}{(6 + (1 \times ((8 \times 5) + 4)))} := \frac{(30 + (9 - (2 - 7)))}{(6 + (1 + (85 - 4)))} := \frac{(30 + (9 \times (2 \times 7)))}{(6 \times (1 \times ((8 + 5) \times 4)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(30 + (9 \times (2 + 7)))}{(6 \times (1 + ((8 \times 5) - 4)))} := \frac{(30 + (9 + (2 - 7)))}{(6 + (1 \times (8 + 54)))} := \frac{(309 - 27)}{(6 \times ((18 \times 5) + 4))}
 \end{aligned}$$

► **45381**
90762

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(((4 \times 5) - 3) \times 8) - 1}{(90 \times (7 - (6 - 2)))} := \frac{(((4 - (5 - 3)) \times 8) + 1)}{(90 - (7 \times (6 + 2)))} := \frac{(((4 + 5) \times (3 + 8)) - 1)}{((90 - 76)^2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((4 + 5) \times 38) + 1)}{((9 \times (0 + 76)) + 2)} := \frac{(((4 + 5) \times 38) - 1)}{((9 \times (0 + 76)) - 2)} := \frac{((4 - (5 - 3)) \times 81)}{(9 \times ((0 \times 7) + (6^2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times ((5 \times 3) + 8)) - 1)}{((90 + (7 - 6)) \times 2)} := \frac{((4 \times (5 - (3 - 8))) - 1)}{(9 - (0 - (7 + 62)))} := \frac{((4 \times (5 \times 3)) - (8 + 1))}{((9 - (0 - (7 \times 6))) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times (5 + (3 \times 8))) + 1)}{((9 \times (0 + ((7 + 6) \times 2)))} := \frac{((4 \times (5 + (3 + 8))) + 1)}{(90 + ((7 \times 6) - 2))} := \frac{((4 \times (5 + (3 - 8))) + 1)}{((9 \times (0 \times 76)) + 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times (5 + 38)) - 1)}{(90 + (7 \times (6^2)))} := \frac{((4 \times (5 - 3))^8 \times 1)}{(((9 - (0 - 7))^6) \times 2)} := \frac{((4 \times (5 - 3)) + 81)}{(9 - (0 - ((7 + 6)^2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 \times 5) + ((3 \times 8) + 1))}{90 \times (7 - 6)^2} := \frac{((4 \times 5) + (3 + (8 \times 1)))}{(((9 + (0 - 7))^6) - 2)} := \frac{((4^{5-3}) - (8 \times 1))}{((9 + (0 - (7 - 6))) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{((4^{5-3}) - (8 + 1))}{(9 + (0 - (7 - (6 \times 2))))} := \frac{((4^{5-3}) + (8 + 1))}{(90 - ((7 \times 6) - 2))} := \frac{((4 + (5 + 3)) \times (8 \times 1))}{((9 - (0 - 7)) \times (6 \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 + (5 + 3)) \times (8 - 1))}{(90 + (76 + 2))} := \frac{((4 + 5) \times (3 + (8 - 1)))}{(90 \times ((7 - 6) \times 2))} := \frac{((4 + 5) \times (38 + 1))}{(9 \times (0 + (76 + 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{((4 + 5) \times (38 - 1))}{(9 \times (0 + (76 - 2)))} := \frac{((4 + 5) \times 381)}{(9 \times (0 + 762))} := \frac{((45 \times (3 + 8)) + 1)}{((9 - (0 - 7)) \times 62)} \\
 &:= \frac{((45 \times 3) - (8 + 1))}{(9 \times (0 + (7 \times (6 - 2))))} := \frac{((45 - 3) \times (8 + 1))}{(9 \times ((7 - 6) \times 2))} := \frac{(4 - ((5 \times (3 - 8)) + 1))}{((9 \times ((0 \times 7) + 6)) + 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (5 - ((3 \times 8) - 1)))}{(4 - (5 - (3 \times (8 \times 1))))} := \frac{(4 - (5 - (3 \times (8 \times 1))))}{(4 - (5 - (3 \times (8 + 1))))} := \frac{((9 \times ((0 \times 7) + 6)) + 2)}{(4 - (5 - (3 \times (8 + 1))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((9 - (0 - (7 + 6))) \times 2)}{(4 - (5 - (3 \times 81)))} := \frac{(90 - ((7 \times 6) + 2))}{(4 - (5 - (3 + (8 \times 1))))} := \frac{(9 - (0 - (7 + (6^2))))}{(4 - (5 - (3 + (8 - 1))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((9 - (0 - (7 + 6)))^2)}{((9 - (0 - (7 + 6)))^2)} := \frac{(9 - (0 - (7 + (6 - 2))))}{(9 \times ((0 \times 76) + 2))} := \frac{(9 \times ((0 \times 76) + 2))}{(4 - (5 + (3 - (8 \times 1))))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 - (5 + (3 - (8 \times 1))))}{(9 - (0 - (7 - (6 + 2))))} := \frac{(9 + (0 - (7 - (6 - 2))))}{((90 - (7 + 6)) \times 2)} := \frac{(90 - (7 + 6)) \times 2}{(4 \times ((5 + 3) \times (8 + 1)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times ((5 + 3) \times (8 + 1)))}{((9 - (0 - 7)) \times (6^2))} := \frac{(4 \times ((5 - 3) \times (8 + 1)))}{(((9 + (0 - 7)) \times 6)^2)} := \frac{(4 \times ((5 - 3)^{8+1}))}{(((9 + (0 - 7))^6)^2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (5 - (3 - (8 + 1))))}{(90 - ((7 - 6) \times 2))} := \frac{(4 \times (5 - (3 - (8 - 1))))}{((9 + (0 - 7)) \times (6^2))} := \frac{(4 \times (5 - (3 - 81)))}{((90 - 7) \times (6 + 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (5 + (3 \times (8 + 1))))}{(9 - 07)^{6+2}} := \frac{(4 \times (5 + (3 + (8 \times 1))))}{((9 - (0 - 7)) \times (6 + 2))} := \frac{(4 \times (53 - (8 \times 1)))}{(9 \times (0 + ((7 \times 6) - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 \times (53 + (8 + 1)))}{(((90 - 7) \times 6) - 2)} := \frac{(4 + (((5 + 3) \times 8) + 1))}{(((9 \times (0 + 7)) + 6) \times 2)} := \frac{(4 + (((5 + 3) \times 8) - 1))}{(90 + ((7 \times 6) + 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + ((5 \times (3 + 8)) - 1))}{(90 + ((7 + 6) \times 2))} := \frac{(4 + ((5 \times 3) - (8 - 1)))}{(9 - (0 - (7 + (6 + 2))))} := \frac{(4 + ((5^3) - (8 \times 1)))}{(90 + (76 \times 2))}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= \frac{(4 + ((5 - 3) \times (8 - 1)))}{(9 \times ((0 \times 7) + (6 - 2)))} := \frac{(4 + ((5 - 3) \times 81))}{((90 + 76) \times 2)} := \frac{(4 + ((5 - 3)^{8-1}))}{((90 + (7 \times 6)) \times 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (5 - (3 - (8 \times 1))))}{(9 - (0 - (7 + (6 \times 2))))} := \frac{(4 + (5 - (3 - (8 + 1))))}{((9 - ((0 \times 7) - 6)) \times 2)} := \frac{(4 + (5 - (3 - 81)))}{(90 + (7 \times (6 \times 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (5 \times (3 + (8 \times 1))))}{(90 + (7 \times (6 - 2)))} := \frac{(4 + (5 \times (3 + (8 - 1))))}{(9 \times ((0 \times 7) + (6 \times 2)))} := \frac{(4 + (5 \times (38 \times 1)))}{((90 + 7) \times (6 - 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (5 + ((3 \times 8) - 1)))}{(9 + (0 - (7 - 62)))} := \frac{(4 + (5 + (3 - (8 - 1))))}{(9 + (0 - (7 - (6 + 2))))} := \frac{(4 + (5 + (3 \times (8 \times 1))))}{(((9 + (0 - 7))^6) + 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 \times (0 + (7 \times (6 + 2))))}{(4 + (5 + (3 \times 81)))} := \frac{(9 + (0 - (7 - (6^2))))}{(4 + (5 + (3 + (8 - 1))))} := \frac{((9 - (0 - 7)) \times 6) - 2}{(4 + (5 + (38 \times 1)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (5 + (38 + 1)))}{((90 - (7 \times 6)) \times 2)} := \frac{(9 + (0 - (7 - (6^2))))}{(90 + ((7 - 6) \times 2))} := \frac{((9 - (0 - 7)) \times 6) + 2}{(4 + (53 - (8 \times 1)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(4 + (53 - (8 - 1)))}{((9 - (0 - (7 - 6)))^2)} := \frac{(45 - (38 + 1))}{(9 - (0 - (7 - (6 - 2))))} := \frac{(45 \times (3 + (8 \times 1)))}{(90 \times (7 + (6 - 2)))} \\
 &:= \frac{(90 \times (7 \times (6 \times 2)))}{(45 \times (3 + 81))} := \frac{((9 \times (0 + 7)) - 6) \times 2}{(45 + (3 + (8 + 1)))} := \frac{(90 + (76 - 2))}{(45 + (38 - 1))} \\
 &:= \frac{(45 + 381)}{(90 + 762)} := \frac{(4538 + 1)}{(9076 + 2)} := \frac{(4538 - 1)}{(9076 - 2)}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.74 91 Equivalent Blocks

$$\begin{aligned}
 \blacktriangleright \frac{30582}{91746} &:= \frac{(((3 - (0 - 5)) \times 8)^2)}{((9 + (1 - 7)) \times (4^6))} := \frac{(((3 - (0 - 5)) \times 8) + 2)}{(9 \times (1 \times ((7 \times 4) - 6)))} := \frac{(((3 \times (0 + 5)) + 8) \times 2)}{((9 + (1 - 7)) \times 46)} \\
 &:= \frac{(((30 - 5) \times 8) + 2)}{((9 \times (17 \times 4)) - 6)} := \frac{(((30 - 5) \times 8) - 2)}{(9 \times (1 \times ((7 + 4) \times 6)))} := \frac{((3 - ((0 \times 5) - 8)) \times 2)}{((9 - (1 - (7 - 4))) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{((9 \times (1 \times (7 \times 4))) + 6)}{((3 - (0 - (5 \times 8))) \times 2)} := \frac{((9 \times (1 + 7)) + (4 \times 6))}{((3 - (0 - (5 + 8))) \times 2)} := \frac{((9 + (1 \times 7)) \times (4 \times 6))}{((3 - (0 - 5)) \times (8 \times 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 - (0 - 5)) \times (8 - 2))}{(91 + (7 + 46))} := \frac{((3 \times ((0 \times 5) + 8))^2)}{(9 \times ((1 + 7) \times (4 \times 6)))} := \frac{((3 \times ((0 \times 5) + 8)) + 2)}{(9 - (1 - (7 \times (4 + 6))))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (0 - (5 - 8)))^2)}{(9 \times (17 + (4 + 6)))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 - (5 - 8))) + 2)}{(9 + ((1 + (7 - 4)) \times 6))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 - (5 - 8))) - 2)}{(9 - ((1 - (7 - 4)) \times 6))} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (0 \times 5)) + (8 \times 2))}{(9 - (1 \times (7 - 46)))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 \times 5)) + (8^2))}{((9 - (1^7)) \times (4 \times 6))} := \frac{((3 \times (0 \times 5)) + (8 + 2))}{((9 - (1 + (7 - 4))) \times 6)} \\
 &:= \frac{((3 \times (0 \times 5)) + 82)}{((9 \times (1 \times (7 \times 4))) - 6)} := \frac{((3 \times (0 + (5 \times 8))) - 2)}{((9 \times (0 + (5 \times 8))) - 2)} := \frac{((9 \times (17 - 4)) + 6)}{((3 \times (0 + (5 + 8))) + 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{((9 \times (17 - 4)) - 6)}{((3 \times (0 + 58)) + 2)} := \frac{((9 \times (1 \times (7 + 4))) - 6)}{((3 \times (0 - 5)) + 82)} := \frac{(9 + (1 + (7 + 46)))}{3^{0 \times 5 + 8} \times 2} \\
 &:= \frac{((91 - (7 - 4)) \times 6)}{((3^{-05+8}) \times 2)} := \frac{(9 + ((1 + 7) \times (4 \times 6)))}{((3^{-05+8}) + 2)} := \frac{((9 \times (1 + (7 - 4))) \times 6)}{((3^{-05+8}) - 2)} \\
 &:= \frac{(9 \times (1 + (7 + (4 + 6))))}{((3^{05}) - (8 \times 2))} := \frac{(9 + ((17 - 4) \times 6))}{((3^{05}) \times (8^2))} := \frac{(9 + (1 \times ((7 + 4) \times 6)))}{((3^{05}) \times (8 + 2))} \\
 &:= \frac{((9 \times (1 + 74)) + 6)}{((3^{05}) \times (8 - 2))} := \frac{((9 - (1 \times (7 - 4)))^6)}{((9 - 1) \times ((7 - 4)^6))} \\
 &:= \frac{((9 \times (1 \times (7 - 4))) \times 6)}{((3 + (0 - (5 - 8)))^2)} := \frac{((30 - (5 + 8)) \times 2)}{((9 \times (1 + (7 + 4))) - 6)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \frac{((30 \times 5) - (8 \times 2))}{(((9 \times (1 \times 7)) + 4) \times 6)} := \frac{((30 \times 5) + (8 \times 2))}{((9 + (1 \times 74)) \times 6)} := \frac{((30 \times 5) + (8 + 2))}{((91 - (7 + 4)) \times 6)} \\
 & := \frac{((30^5) \times (8 + 2))}{((9 + (17 + 4))^6)} := \frac{((30 + 5) \times (8 \times 2))}{((9 + 1) \times (7 \times (4 \times 6)))} := \frac{((30 + 5) \times (8 - 2))}{(9 \times (1 \times (7 \times (4 + 6))))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 - ((0 \times 5) - (8 \times 2)))}{(91 - ((7 \times 4) + 6))} := \frac{(3 - ((0 \times 5) - (8 + 2)))}{(9 - (1 - (7 + (4 \times 6))))} := \frac{(3 - ((0 \times 5) - 82))}{((9 \times (1 + (7 \times 4))) - 6)} \\
 & := \frac{(91 - ((0 \times 58) - 2))}{(9 + (1 + (7 + (4 - 6))))} := \frac{(9 - (1 - (7 + (4 \times 6))))}{(3 - (0 - (5 - (8 - 2))))} := \frac{((9 \times (1 + (7 \times 4))) - 6)}{(3 - (0 - (5 \times (8 + 2))))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 - (0 - (5 + (8 \times 2))))}{((9 + (1 \times (7 - (4 + 6))))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (5 + (8^2))))}{(9 + (1 \times (7 - (4 + 6))))} := \frac{(91 + (74 - 6))}{(3 - (0 - (5 + (8 + 2))))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 - (0 - (5 + (8 \times 2))))}{((9 + (1 \times (7 - 4))) \times 6)} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (5 + (8^2))))}{(9 \times ((1 + (7 - 4)) \times 6))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (5 + (8 + 2))))}{(9 \times (1 + (7 + (4 - 6))))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 - (0 - (5 + (8 - 2))))}{((9 + (1 - (7 - 4))) \times 6)} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (5 + 82)))}{(9 \times ((1^7) + 4) \times 6)} := \frac{(3 - (0 - (58 - 2)))}{(9 + (1 \times (7 \times (4 \times 6))))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 - (0 \times (5 - 82)))}{(9 \times (1^{746}))} := \frac{(3 - (0 - 582))}{(9 + 1746)} := \frac{(3 \times ((0 - (5 - 8))^2))}{(9 \times (1 \times (7 - (4 - 6))))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 \times ((0 \times 5) + (8 + 2)))}{(9 \times (1 + (7 - (4 - 6))))} := \frac{(3 \times ((0 \times 5) + 82))}{(9 + (1 \times ((7 - 4)^6)))} := \frac{(3 \times ((0 \times 58) + 2))}{(9 + (1 \times (7 - (4 - 6))))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 \times (0 - (5 - (8 + 2))))}{(9 \times (1 \times (7 + (4 - 6))))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + ((5 \times 8) + 2)))}{((91 - (7 \times 4)) \times 6)} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + ((5 \times 8) - 2)))}{(9 \times (((1 + 7) \times 4) + 6))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 \times (0 + ((5 + 8) \times 2)))}{(9 \times (((1 + 7) \times 4) - 6))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + ((5 + 8)^2))}{(9 \times (1 + (7 \times (4 \times 6))))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (5 \times (8 \times 2))))}{(9 \times (1 \times (74 + 6)))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (5^{8-2})))}{(9 \times (((1^7) + 4)^6)} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (5 + (8 \times 2))))}{(9 + (174 + 6))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (5 + (8^2))))}{(9 \times (1 + (74 - 6)))} \\
 & := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (5 + (8 + 2))))}{(9 \times (1 - (7 \times (4 - 6))))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (5 + (8 - 2))))}{(9 \times ((1^7) + (4 + 6)))} := \frac{(3 \times (0 + (58 - 2)))}{((9 + (1 + 74)) \times 6)} \\
 & := \frac{3^{(-05+8)^2}}{3^{0 \times 58+2}} := \frac{3^{05+8+2}}{3^{-05+8+2}} \\
 & := \frac{(9 \times (1 \times (7 + (4 - 6))))}{(3 + ((0 - (5 - 8))^2))} := \frac{(9 + (1 + (7 + (4 + 6))))}{(3 + ((0 \times 58) - 2))} := \frac{(9 \times (1 + (74 + 6)))}{(3 + (0 - (5 - (8 + 2))))} \\
 & := \frac{(9 \times (1 - (7 - (4 + 6))))}{(3 + (0 - (5 - (8 - 2))))} := \frac{(9 - (1 + (7 + (4 - 6))))}{(3 + (0 - (5 - 82)))} := \frac{(9 + (1 - (7 \times (4 - 6))))}{(30 - (5 - (8^2)))} \\
 & := \frac{(9 - (1 \times (7 - (4 + 6))))}{(30 - (5 - (8 + 2)))} := \frac{((9 + (1^7)) \times (4 \times 6))}{(30 \times (5 + (8 - 2)))} := \frac{((9 \times (1 + (7 \times 4))) + 6)}{(30 + (5 \times (8 \times 2)))} \\
 & := \frac{((9 \times (1 \times (7 + 4))) + 6)}{(30 + (5 \times (8 - 2)))} := \frac{((91 + 74) \times 6)}{(30 + (5 + (8 \times 2)))} := \frac{(9 - (1 - (7 \times 46)))}{(305 - (8^2))} \\
 & := \frac{(30 + (5 \times (8 - 2)))}{((9 + (17 + 4)) \times 6)} := \frac{(30 + (5 + (8 \times 2)))}{(9 \times (1 \times (7 + (4 + 6))))} := \frac{(305 - (8^2))}{((9 \times (1 \times (7 - 4))) - 6)} \\
 & := \frac{305 + 8 \times 2}{917 + 46} := \frac{305 - 82}{9 \times (1 + 74) - 6} := \frac{3058 + 2}{9174 + 6} \\
 & := \frac{3058 - 2}{9174 - 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

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